

Semi-Selfie Numbers¹.

Inder J. Taneja²

Abstract

Author studied many ways of writing **selfie numbers** [13]. There are numbers very much near to **selfie-number**, but are not **selfie numbers**. These types of numbers, referred as **semi-selfie numbers**, where numbers are written in terms of expressions with positive and negative signs having same digits on both sides of the expressions, except the power values. This paper brings **semi-selfie numbers** in different situations. In some situations, they are expressed with positive sign, and positive and negative signs. The work is limited up to 11-digits numbers. This work is revised, enlarged and combined version of author's previous two works [17, 19].

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¹It is revised and enlarged version of author's previous works: <http://rgmia.org/papers/v20/v20a83.pdf> and <http://rgmia.org/papers/v20/v20a116.pdf> done in 2017.

²Formerly, Professor of Mathematics, Federal University of Santa Catarina, Florianópolis, SC, Brazil (1978-2012). Also worked at Delhi University, India (1976-1978). **E-mail:** ijaneja@gmail.com; **Web-site:** <https://inderjtaneja.com>; **Twitter:** @IJTANEJA; **Instagram:** @crazynumbers.

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1 Selfie Numbers

Recently, author studied different ways of expressing numbers in such a way that both sides are with same digits. One side is with number, and another side is an expression formed by same digits with some operations. These types of numbers we call **selfie numbers**. Some times they are called as **wild narcissistic numbers**. These numbers are represented by their own digits by use of certain operations. Subsections below give different ways of writing **selfie numbers**. See below some examples:

$$\begin{aligned}
 936 &:= (\sqrt{9})!^3 + 6! &&= 6! + (3!)^{\sqrt{9}} \\
 1296 &:= \sqrt{(1+2)!^9/6} &&= 6^{(\sqrt{9}+2-1)} \\
 2896 &:= 2 \times (8 + (\sqrt{9})!! + 6!) &&= (6! + (\sqrt{9})!! + 8) \times 2 \\
 331779 &:= 3 + (31 - 7)^{\sqrt{7+9}} &&= \sqrt{9} + (7 \times 7 - 1)^3 \times 3 \\
 342995 &:= (3^4 - 2 - 9)^{\sqrt{9}} - 5 &&= -5 + (-9 + 9^2 - \sqrt{4})^3 \\
 759375 &:= (-7 + 59 - 37)^5 &&= (5 + 7 + 3)^{\sqrt{9}-5+7} \\
 759381 &:= 7 + (5 \times \sqrt{9})^{-3+8} - 1 &&= -1 + (8 \times 3 - 9)^5 + 7
 \end{aligned}$$

Examples given above are with **factorial** and **square-root** [11, 12]. First column numbers are in **digit's order** and second columns are in **reverse order of digits**. For details refer author's work [4, 5, 6, 8, 9, 10]. Still, one can have interesting results just with **factorial** [10]. See below:

$1463 = -1! + 4! + 6! + 3!!$	$361469 = 3! - 6! - 1! + 4! - 6! + 9!$
$10077 = -1! - 0! - 0! + 7! + 7!$	$364292 = 3!! + 6! - 4! - 2! + 9! - 2!$
$40585 = 4! + 0! + 5! + 8! + 5!$	$397584 = -3!! + 9! - 7! + 5! + 8! + 4!$
$80518 = 8! - 0! - 5! - 1! + 8!$	$398173 = 3! + 9! + 8! + 1! - 7! + 3!$
$317489 = -3! - 1! - 7! - 4! - 8! + 9!$	$408937 = -4! + 0! + 8! + 9! + 3!! + 7!$
$352797 = -3! + 5 - 2! - 7! + 9! - 7!$	$715799 = -7! - 1! + 5! - 7! + 9! + 9!$
$357592 = -3! - 5! - 7! - 5! + 9! - 2!$	$720599 = -7! - 2! + 0! - 5! + 9! + 9!$
$357941 = 3! + 5! - 7! + 9! - 4! - 1!$	

$$\begin{aligned} 145 &= 1! + 4! + 5! \\ 733 &= 7 + 3!! + 3! \\ 5177 &= 5! + 17 + 7! \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 363239 &= 36 + 323 + 9! \\ 363269 &= 363 + 26 + 9! \\ 403199 &= 40319 + 9!. \end{aligned}$$

More studies and summary of work on numbers in different situations, refer author's work [13, 14, ?].

2 Semi-Selfie Numbers

Before defining the idea of **Semi-Selfie Numbers**, let us consider following historical example (Madachy [3], p.167-170, and Heinz [1]):

$$\begin{aligned} 81 &:= (8 + 1)^2 \\ 512 &:= (5 + 1 + 2)^3 \\ 4913 &:= (4 + 9 + 1 + 3)^3 \\ 17576 &:= (1 + 7 + 5 + 7 + 6)^3 \\ 234256 &:= (2 + 3 + 4 + 2 + 5 + 6)^4 \\ 1679616 &:= (1 + 6 + 7 + 9 + 6 + 1 + 6)^4 \\ 17210368 &:= (1 + 7 + 2 + 1 + 0 + 3 + 6 + 8)^5 \\ 205962976 &:= (2 + 0 + 5 + 9 + 6 + 2 + 9 + 7 + 6)^5 \\ 8303765625 &:= (8 + 3 + 0 + 3 + 7 + 6 + 5 + 6 + 2 + 5)^6 \\ 24794911296 &:= (2 + 4 + 7 + 9 + 4 + 9 + 1 + 1 + 2 + 9 + 6)^6 \\ 271818611107 &:= (2 + 7 + 1 + 8 + 1 + 8 + 6 + 1 + 1 + 1 + 0 + 7)^7 \\ 6722988818432 &:= (6 + 7 + 2 + 2 + 9 + 8 + 8 + 8 + 1 + 8 + 4 + 3 + 2)^7 \\ 72301961339136 &:= (7 + 2 + 3 + 0 + 1 + 9 + 6 + 1 + 3 + 3 + 9 + 1 + 3 + 6)^8 \\ 248155780267521 &:= (2 + 4 + 8 + 1 + 5 + 5 + 7 + 8 + 0 + 2 + 6 + 7 + 5 + 2 + 1)^8 \end{aligned} \tag{1}$$

The above representation (1) is in such a way that the both sides we have same digits except the power. Let us call it **Semi-Selfie Numbers**. *This means that semi-selfie numbers are understood as numbers having the same digit's order on both side, except the power.* The above numbers are separated by a single digit and are with positive signs, while in our case, it may have negative sign and not necessarily a single digit. See some examples, below:

• Examples of Semi-Selfie Numbers

$$\begin{aligned} 20736 &:= (2 + 07 - 3 + 6)^4 \\ 21952 &:= (2 + 19 + 5 + 2)^3 \\ 494209 &:= (494 + 209)^2 \\ 998001 &:= (998 + 001)^2 \\ 3759161344 &:= (-37 - 5 + 9 + 1 + 61344)^2 \\ 3767287616 &:= (-3 + 76 + 728 + 761 - 6)^3 \end{aligned}$$

The aim of this work is bring similar kind of numbers but with positive and negative signs. Also, the idea is to extend for any number of digits instead of single digit, for examples some numbers appearing in (1) can also be written as

$$\begin{aligned}
 512 &:= (5 + 1 + 2)^3 = (5 - 1 - 2)^9 \\
 234256 &:= (2 + 3 + 4 + 2 + 5 + 6)^4 = (-234 + 256)^4 \\
 1679616 &:= (1 + 6 + 7 + 9 + 6 + 1 + 6)^4 = (1 + 679 + 616)^2 \\
 17210368 &:= (1 + 7 + 2 + 1 + 0 + 3 + 6 + 8)^5 = (1 + 72 - 1 - 036 - 8)^5 \\
 205962976 &:= (2 + 0 + 5 + 9 + 6 + 2 + 9 + 7 + 6)^5 = (2 - 05 + 96 + 29 - 76)^5 \\
 8303765625 &:= (8 + 3 + 0 + 3 + 7 + 6 + 5 + 6 + 2 + 5)^6 = (83 + 037 + 6 - 56 - 25)^6 \\
 24794911296 &:= (2 + 4 + 7 + 9 + 4 + 9 + 1 + 1 + 2 + 9 + 6)^6 = (247 + 9 + 4 + 91 - 1 - 296)^6. \tag{2}
 \end{aligned}$$

Below are more examples divided in two subsections. One only for positive sign and another for positive and negative signs. Results are up to 11-digits numbers. This work is reversed and enlarged version of author's previous two works [16, 19]. In [18] interesting patterns with semi-selfie numbers are presented. This work brings detailed study up to 11 digits numbers. In the end the complete list is also given. It interesting to observe that the numbers [68719476736](#) in 11-digits is represented in [1054](#) different ways. In case of 10-digits numbers, the number [4294967296](#) is represented in [482](#) different ways. In future, we shall try to bring results for 12-digits numbers.

3 Equal Digits Expressions

This section brings equal digits expressions, such as 1 by 1, 2 by 2, 3 by 3, etc.

3.1 Single Digit

In the representation (1), not all the numbers are included. The representation (1) brings only one possibility in each case, while below we have multiple choices. The work is limited to 11 digits. We have divided it in two subsections. One only with positive sign and another with positive and negative signs.

3.1.1 Positive Sign

$$\begin{aligned}
 81 &:= (8 + 1)^2 \\
 512 &:= (5 + 1 + 2)^3 \\
 2401 &:= (2 + 4 + 0 + 1)^4 \\
 4913 &:= (4 + 9 + 1 + 3)^3 \\
 5832 &:= (5 + 8 + 3 + 2)^3 \\
 17576 &:= (1 + 7 + 5 + 7 + 6)^3 \\
 19683 &:= (1 + 9 + 6 + 8 + 3)^3 \\
 234256 &:= (2 + 3 + 4 + 2 + 5 + 6)^4 \\
 390625 &:= (3 + 9 + 0 + 6 + 2 + 5)^4 \\
 614656 &:= (6 + 1 + 4 + 6 + 5 + 6)^4 \\
 1679616 &:= (1 + 6 + 7 + 9 + 6 + 1 + 6)^4 \\
 17210368 &:= (1 + 7 + 2 + 1 + 0 + 3 + 6 + 8)^5 \\
 34012224 &:= (3 + 4 + 0 + 1 + 2 + 2 + 2 + 4)^6 \\
 52521875 &:= (5 + 2 + 5 + 2 + 1 + 8 + 7 + 5)^5 \\
 60466176 &:= (6 + 0 + 4 + 6 + 6 + 1 + 7 + 6)^5
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 205962976 &:= (2+0+5+9+6+2+9+7+6)^5 \\
 612220032 &:= (6+1+2+2+2+0+0+3+2)^7 \\
 8303765625 &:= (8+3+0+3+7+6+5+6+2+5)^6 \\
 10460353203 &:= (1+0+4+6+0+3+5+3+2+0+3)^7 \\
 24794911296 &:= (2+4+7+9+4+9+1+1+2+9+6)^6 \\
 27512614111 &:= (2+7+5+1+2+6+1+4+1+1+1)^7 \\
 52523350144 &:= (5+2+5+2+3+3+5+0+1+4+4)^7 \\
 68719476736 &:= (6+8+7+1+9+4+7+6+7+3+6)^6
 \end{aligned}$$

3.1.2 Positive and Negative Signs

Below are numbers similar to (1), i.e., single digits representations, but with **positive and negative signs**:

$$\begin{aligned}
 64 &:= (6-4)^6 & 279936 &:= (2+7+9-9+3-6)^7 \\
 196 &:= (-1+9+6)^2 & 371293 &:= (3+7-1-2+9-3)^5 \\
 243 &:= (2+4-3)^5 & 390625 &:= (3-9+0-6+2+5)^8 \\
 512 &:= (5-1-2)^9 & 823543 &:= (8-2+3+5-4-3)^7 \\
 1296 &:= (1+2+9-6)^4 & 1419857 &:= (1+4+1-9+8+5+7)^5 \\
 1728 &:= (-1+7-2+8)^3 & 1594323 &:= (1+5-9+4-3+2+3)^{13} \\
 2048 &:= (-2+0-4+8)^{11} & 1679616 &:= (1+6+7-9-6+1+6)^8 \\
 2197 &:= (-2-1+9+7)^3 & 2097152 &:= (2+0-9+7-1+5-2)^{21} \\
 3125 &:= (3-1-2+5)^5 & &:= (2+0+9-7+1+5-2)^7 \\
 8192 &:= (8+1-9+2)^{13} & 2476099 &:= (2+4+7+6+0+9-9)^5 \\
 15625 &:= (1+5+6-2-5)^6 & 4782969 &:= (4+7+8+2-9+6-9)^7 \\
 16384 &:= (1-6+3+8-4)^{14} & &:= (4-7-8+2+9-6+9)^{14} \\
 &:= (1-6-3+8+4)^7 & 4826809 &:= (-4+8+2+6-8+0+9)^6 \\
 19683 &:= (1-9+6+8-3)^9 & 5764801 &:= (5+7+6-4-8+0+1)^8 \\
 20736 &:= (2+0+7-3+6)^4 & 6436343 &:= (6+4+3+6-3+4+3)^5 \\
 32768 &:= (3-2-7+6+8)^5 & 7962624 &:= (7+9-6+2+6+2+4)^5 \\
 &:= (-3-2-7+6+8)^{15} & 10077696 &:= (1+0+0+7+7+6-9-6)^9 \\
 38416 &:= (3+8-4+1+6)^4 & 11390625 &:= (1+1+3+9+0-6+2+5)^6 \\
 59049 &:= (5+9+0+4-9)^5 & 24137569 &:= (2+4-1+3+7+5+6-9)^6 \\
 78125 &:= (7-8-1+2+5)^7 & 35831808 &:= (3+5+8-3-1+8+0-8)^7 \\
 83521 &:= (8+3+5+2-1)^4 & 43046721 &:= (4-3+0+4-6+7-2-1)^{16} \\
 & & &:= (4+3+0+4-6+7-2-1)^8 \\
 131072 &:= (1-3-1+0+7-2)^{17} & 47045881 &:= (4+7+0+4+5+8-8-1)^6 \\
 177147 &:= (1+7+7-1-4-7)^{11} & 67108864 &:= (6+7-1+0+8-8-6-4)^{26} \\
 279841 &:= (2+7+9+8-4+1)^4 & &:= (6+7+1+0+8-8-6-4)^{13}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$129140163 := (1 + 2 + 9 - 1 - 4 + 0 - 1 - 6 + 3)^{17}$$

$$170859375 := (1 - 7 + 0 - 8 + 5 + 9 + 3 + 7 + 5)^7$$

$$191102976 := (1 + 9 + 1 + 1 + 0 + 2 + 9 + 7 - 6)^6$$

$$282475249 := (2 + 8 + 2 + 4 + 7 - 5 + 2 - 4 - 9)^{10}$$

$$308915776 := (3 + 0 + 8 - 9 - 1 + 5 + 7 + 7 + 6)^6$$

$$387420489 := (3 + 8 + 7 + 4 + 2 + 0 + 4 + 8 - 9)^6$$

$$387420489 := (3 + 8 + 7 - 4 - 2 + 0 - 4 - 8 + 9)^9$$

$$:= (3 + 8 + 7 + 4 + 2 + 0 - 4 - 8 - 9)^{18}$$

$$410338673 := (4 + 1 + 0 + 3 + 3 + 8 - 6 + 7 - 3)^7$$

$$429981696 := (4 + 2 + 9 + 9 + 8 + 1 - 6 - 9 - 6)^8$$

$$594823321 := (5 + 9 + 4 + 8 + 2 + 3 - 3 + 2 - 1)^6$$

$$893871739 := (8 + 9 + 3 + 8 - 7 - 1 - 7 - 3 + 9)^7$$

$$:= (4 + 2 + 9 + 4 + 9 - 6 - 7 + 2 - 9 - 6)^{32}$$

$$6975757441 := (6 + 9 + 7 + 5 - 7 + 5 - 7 + 4 - 4 - 1)^8$$

$$7256313856 := (7 + 2 + 5 + 6 + 3 - 1 + 3 + 8 + 5 + 6)^6$$

$$8589934592 := (8 + 5 + 8 + 9 - 9 + 3 - 4 - 5 - 9 + 2)^{11}$$

$$:= (8 + 5 + 8 + 9 - 9 - 3 - 4 - 5 - 9 + 2)^{33}$$

$$9474296896 := (9 + 4 + 7 + 4 + 2 + 9 + 6 + 8 - 9 + 6)^6$$

$$10460353203 := (1 + 0 + 4 - 6 + 0 + 3 + 5 - 3 + 2 + 0 - 3)^{21}$$

$$13060694016 := (1 + 3 + 0 + 6 + 0 + 6 - 9 + 4 + 0 + 1 - 6)^{13}$$

$$13060694016 := (1 + 3 + 0 + 6 + 0 - 6 - 9 + 4 + 0 + 1 + 6)^{13}$$

$$13492928512 := (1 + 3 + 4 + 9 + 2 + 9 + 2 - 8 + 5 - 1 + 2)^7$$

$$13841287201 := (1 + 3 + 8 + 4 + 1 + 2 - 8 - 7 + 2 + 0 + 1)^{12}$$

$$20661046784 := (2 + 0 + 6 + 6 + 1 + 0 + 4 + 6 - 7 - 8 + 4)^9$$

$$25937424601 := (2 + 5 + 9 + 3 + 7 - 4 - 2 - 4 - 6 + 0 + 1)^{10}$$

$$31381059609 := (3 + 1 + 3 + 8 + 1 + 0 + 5 - 9 + 6 + 0 - 9)^{11}$$

$$:= (3 + 1 + 3 + 8 - 1 + 0 - 5 + 9 - 6 + 0 - 9)^{22}$$

$$68719476736 := (6 - 8 - 7 + 1 - 9 + 4 + 7 + 6 + 7 + 3 + 6)^9$$

$$:= (6 - 8 - 7 - 1 - 9 + 4 + 7 + 6 + 7 - 3 + 6)^{12}$$

$$:= (6 - 8 - 7 - 1 + 9 - 4 - 7 + 6 + 7 - 3 + 6)^{18}$$

$$:= (6 - 8 - 7 - 1 - 9 + 4 + 7 - 6 + 7 + 3 + 6)^{36}$$

$$78364164096 := (7 + 8 + 3 + 6 + 4 + 1 + 6 + 4 + 0 - 9 + 6)^7$$

$$:= (7 + 8 + 3 + 6 - 4 - 1 + 6 - 4 + 0 - 9 - 6)^{14}$$

$$94931877133 := (9 + 4 + 9 + 3 + 1 - 8 + 7 + 7 - 1 + 3 + 3)^7$$

$$1220703125 := (1 + 2 + 2 + 0 + 7 + 0 - 3 - 1 + 2 - 5)^{13}$$

$$1475789056 := (1 + 4 + 7 + 5 + 7 - 8 + 9 + 0 - 5 - 6)^8$$

$$1977326743 := (1 + 9 + 7 + 7 - 3 - 2 - 6 - 7 + 4 - 3)^{11}$$

$$2357947691 := (2 + 3 + 5 + 7 + 9 - 4 - 7 + 6 - 9 - 1)^9$$

$$2494357888 := (2 + 4 + 9 + 4 - 3 + 5 - 7 - 8 + 8 + 8)^7$$

$$2562890625 := (2 + 5 + 6 + 2 + 8 - 9 + 0 - 6 + 2 + 5)^8$$

$$3404825447 := (3 + 4 + 0 + 4 + 8 + 2 - 5 + 4 - 4 + 7)^7$$

$$3486784401 := (3 + 4 + 8 - 6 + 7 - 8 + 4 - 4 + 0 + 1)^{10}$$

$$:= (3 + 4 + 8 - 6 - 7 + 8 - 4 - 4 + 0 + 1)^{20}$$

$$3518743761 := (3 + 5 + 1 + 8 + 7 + 4 - 3 + 7 + 6 + 1)^6$$

$$4294967296 := (4 + 2 + 9 + 4 + 9 - 6 - 7 - 2 + 9 - 6)^8$$

$$:= (4 + 2 + 9 + 4 - 9 + 6 - 7 - 2 - 9 + 6)^{16}$$

3.2 Two-Digits

3.2.1 Positive Sign

$$1000 := (10 + 00)^3$$

$$2025 := (20 + 25)^2$$

$$3025 := (30 + 25)^2$$

$$9801 := (98 + 01)^2$$

$$100000 := (10 + 00 + 00)^5$$

$$10000000 := (10 + 00 + 00 + 00)^7$$

$$20151121 := (20 + 15 + 11 + 21)^4$$

$$1000000000 := (10 + 00 + 00 + 00 + 00)^9$$

$$1222830961 := (12 + 22 + 83 + 09 + 61)^4$$

$$1536953616 := (15 + 36 + 95 + 36 + 16)^4$$

$$1568239201 := (15 + 68 + 23 + 92 + 01)^4$$

$$2897022976 := (28 + 97 + 02 + 29 + 76)^4$$

$$3486784401 := (34 + 86 + 78 + 44 + 01)^4$$

$$4097152081 := (40 + 97 + 15 + 20 + 81)^4$$

$$6690585616 := (66 + 90 + 58 + 56 + 16)^4$$

3.2.2 Positive and Negative Signs

$$\begin{aligned}195112 &:= (19 + 51 - 12)^3 & & := (-21 + 76 - 78 + 23 + 36)^6 \\456533 &:= (45 + 65 - 33)^3 & & 3486784401 := (-34 - 86 + 78 + 44 + 01)^{20} \\20511149 &:= (20 - 51 + 11 + 49)^5 & & 4294967296 := (42 + 94 - 96 + 72 - 96)^8 \\24137569 &:= (24 - 13 + 75 - 69)^6 & & := (42 + 94 + 96 - 72 + 96)^4 \\81450625 &:= (81 + 45 - 06 - 25)^4 & & 5584059449 := (55 + 84 - 05 - 94 + 49)^5 \\1358954496 &:= (-13 + 58 + 95 - 44 + 96)^4 & & 6240321451 := (62 - 40 + 32 - 14 + 51)^5 \\1838265625 &:= (18 - 38 - 26 + 56 + 25)^6 & & 9039207968 := (90 + 39 - 20 - 79 + 68)^5 \\2176782336 &:= (21 + 76 - 78 + 23 - 36)^{12} & & 9509900499 := (95 + 09 + 90 + 04 - 99)^5 \\& := (21 - 76 + 78 - 23 + 36)^6 & & := (95 - 09 - 90 + 04 + 99)^5\end{aligned}$$

3.3 Three-Digits

3.3.1 Positive Sign

$$\begin{aligned}494209 &:= (494 + 209)^2 \\998001 &:= (998 + 001)^2\end{aligned}$$

3.3.2 Positive and Negative Signs

$$\begin{aligned}132496 &:= (-132 + 496)^2 & & 360944128 := (-360 + 944 + 128)^3 \\234256 &:= (-234 + 256)^4 & & 365525875 := (365 - 525 + 875)^3 \\456533 &:= (-456 + 533)^3 & & 384240583 := (384 - 240 + 583)^3 \\474552 &:= (-474 + 552)^3 & & 429981696 := (429 - 981 + 696)^4 \\105413504 &:= (105 + 413 - 504)^7 & & 547981281 := (-547 + 981 - 281)^4 \\188132517 &:= (188 - 132 + 517)^3 & & 605495736 := (605 - 495 + 736)^3 \\258474853 &:= (258 - 474 + 853)^3 & & 786330467 := (786 - 330 + 467)^3 \\312900721 &:= (312 - 900 + 721)^4\end{aligned}$$

3.4 Four-Digits

3.4.1 Positive Sign

$$\begin{aligned}24502500 &:= (2450 + 2500)^2 & & 60481729 := (6048 + 1729)^2 \\25502500 &:= (2550 + 2500)^2 & & 99980001 := (9998 + 0001)^2 \\52881984 &:= (5288 + 1984)^2\end{aligned}$$

3.4.2 Positive and Negative Signs

$$69426531 := (6942 - 6531)^3$$

3.5 Five-Digits

3.5.1 Positive Sign

$$6049417284 := (60494 + 17284)^2$$

$$9999800001 := (99998 + 00001)^2$$

$$6832014336 := (68320 + 14336)^2$$

$$9048004641 := (90480 + 04641)^2$$

4 Equal Terms Expressions

This section deals with expressions with fixed term expressions. Initially the results are with two-terms expressions.

4.1 Two-Terms

4.1.1 Positive Sign

$$81 := (8 + 1)^2$$

$$4941729 := (494 + 1729)^2$$

$$100 := (10 + 0)^2$$

$$7441984 := (744 + 1984)^2$$

$$1000 := (10 + 00)^3$$

$$10000000 := (10 + 000000)^7$$

$$2025 := (20 + 25)^2$$

$$23804641 := (238 + 04641)^2$$

$$3025 := (30 + 25)^2$$

$$24502500 := (2450 + 2500)^2$$

$$9801 := (98 + 01)^2$$

$$25502500 := (2550 + 2500)^2$$

$$10000 := (10 + 000)^4$$

$$28005264 := (28 + 005264)^2$$

$$10000 := (100 + 00)^2$$

$$52881984 := (5288 + 1984)^2$$

$$88209 := (88 + 209)^2$$

$$60481729 := (6048 + 1729)^2$$

$$99980001 := (9998 + 0001)^2$$

$$100000 := (10 + 0000)^5$$

$$100000000 := (10 + 0000000)^8$$

$$494209 := (494 + 209)^2$$

$$100000000 := (100 + 000000)^4$$

$$998001 := (998 + 001)^2$$

$$100000000 := (10000 + 0000)^2$$

$$1000000 := (10 + 00000)^6$$

$$300814336 := (3008 + 14336)^2$$

$$1000000 := (100 + 0000)^3$$

$$493817284 := (4938 + 17284)^2$$

$$1000000 := (1000 + 000)^2$$

$$1000000000 := (10 + 00000000)^9$$

$$1000000000 := (1000 + 000000)^3$$

$$1518037444 := (1518 + 037444)^2$$

$$6049417284 := (60494 + 17284)^2$$

$$6832014336 := (68320 + 14336)^2$$

$$9048004641 := (90480 + 04641)^2$$

$$1000000000 := (10 + 00000000)^{10}$$

$$1000000000 := (100 + 00000000)^5$$

$$1000000000 := (100000 + 00000)^2$$

$$20408122449 := (20408 + 122449)^2$$

$$21948126201 := (21948 + 126201)^2$$

$$33058148761 := (33058 + 148761)^2$$

$$35010152100 := (35010 + 152100)^2$$

$$43470165025 := (43470 + 165025)^2$$

4.1.2 Positive and Negative Signs

$$64 := (6 - 4)^6$$

$$121 := (12 - 1)^2$$

$$6084 := (-6 + 084)^2$$

$$10201 := (102 - 01)^2$$

$$82369 := (-82 + 369)^2$$

$$132496 := (-132 + 496)^2$$

$$234256 := (-234 + 256)^4$$

$$456533 := (-456 + 533)^3$$

$$474552 := (-474 + 552)^3$$

$$1002001 := (1002 - 001)^2$$

$$1162084 := (1162 - 084)^2$$

$$1201216 := (-120 + 1216)^2$$

$$1656369 := (1656 - 369)^2$$

$$1860496 := (1860 - 496)^2$$

$$69426531 := (6942 - 6531)^3$$

$$100020001 := (10002 - 0001)^2$$

$$123121216 := (12312 - 1216)^2$$

$$330621489 := (-3306 + 21489)^2$$

$$10000200001 := (100002 - 00001)^2$$

$$13967221489 := (139672 - 21489)^2$$

4.2 Three-Terms

4.2.1 Positive Sign

$$512 := (5 + 1 + 2)^3$$

$$1296 := (1 + 29 + 6)^2$$

$$2401 := (2 + 4 + 01)^4$$

$$6724 := (6 + 72 + 4)^2$$

$$8281 := (82 + 8 + 1)^2$$

$$55225 := (5 + 5 + 225)^2$$

$$91125 := (9 + 11 + 25)^3$$

$$136900 := (1 + 369 + 00)^2$$

$$143641 := (14 + 364 + 1)^2$$

$$171396 := (17 + 1 + 396)^2$$

$$455625 := (45 + 5 + 625)^2$$

$$571536 := (5 + 715 + 36)^2$$

$$627264 := (62 + 726 + 4)^2$$

$$826281 := (826 + 2 + 81)^2$$

$$842724 := (842 + 72 + 4)^2$$

$$929296 := (929 + 29 + 6)^2$$

$$980100 := (980 + 10 + 0)^2$$

$$\begin{aligned} 982081 &:= (982 + 08 + 1)^2 \\ 1679616 &:= (1 + 679 + 616)^2 \\ 2406104 &:= (24 + 06 + 104)^3 \\ 2896804 &:= (2 + 896 + 804)^2 \\ 3175524 &:= (3 + 1755 + 24)^2 \\ 11329956 &:= (11 + 3299 + 56)^2 \\ 13293316 &:= (1 + 329 + 3316)^2 \\ 13557124 &:= (1 + 3557 + 124)^2 \\ 17073424 &:= (1 + 707 + 3424)^2 \\ 24068836 &:= (2 + 4068 + 836)^2 \\ 25502500 &:= (25 + 5025 + 00)^2 \\ 26198073 &:= (26 + 198 + 073)^3 \\ 26512201 &:= (26 + 5122 + 01)^2 \\ 46676224 &:= (46 + 6762 + 24)^2 \\ 56896849 &:= (5 + 689 + 6849)^2 \\ 70829056 &:= (70 + 8290 + 56)^2 \\ 76860289 &:= (76 + 8602 + 89)^2 \\ 78428736 &:= (78 + 42 + 8736)^2 \\ 84787264 &:= (8478 + 726 + 4)^2 \\ 86955625 &:= (8695 + 5 + 625)^2 \\ 91891396 &:= (9189 + 1 + 396)^2 \\ 92563641 &:= (9256 + 364 + 1)^2 \\ 95355225 &:= (9535 + 5 + 225)^2 \\ 98029801 &:= (98 + 02 + 9801)^2 \\ 98029801 &:= (9802 + 98 + 01)^2 \\ 98903025 &:= (9890 + 30 + 25)^2 \\ 99102025 &:= (9910 + 20 + 25)^2 \\ 99800100 &:= (9980 + 010 + 0)^2 \\ 99820081 &:= (9982 + 008 + 1)^2 \\ 149377284 &:= (1 + 4937 + 7284)^2 \\ 161976529 &:= (1 + 6197 + 6529)^2 \\ 298287441 &:= (2 + 9828 + 7441)^2 \\ 480048687 &:= (48 + 0048 + 687)^3 \\ 494217361 &:= (494 + 21736 + 1)^2 \\ 918330048 &:= (91 + 833 + 0048)^3 \\ 128000000 &:= (12 + 8 + 0000000)^7 \\ 1358291025 &:= (1 + 35829 + 1025)^2 \\ 1693240201 &:= (16 + 932 + 40201)^2 \\ 2141745841 &:= (21 + 417 + 45841)^2 \\ 2380464100 &:= (2380 + 46410 + 0)^2 \\ 2384857225 &:= (238 + 48572 + 25)^2 \\ 2505002500 &:= (25 + 050025 + 00)^2 \\ 2560108032 &:= (256 + 01080 + 32)^3 \\ 2800526400 &:= (280 + 052640 + 0)^2 \\ 2805291225 &:= (28 + 052912 + 25)^2 \\ 2853162225 &:= (28 + 53162 + 225)^2 \\ 4181062131 &:= (418 + 1062 + 131)^3 \\ 5906076201 &:= (590 + 60 + 76201)^2 \\ 5947648641 &:= (594 + 76486 + 41)^2 \\ 6580129924 &:= (65 + 80129 + 924)^2 \\ 7261084944 &:= (7 + 261 + 084944)^2 \\ 8862527881 &:= (8 + 86252 + 7881)^2 \\ 9849371536 &:= (98493 + 715 + 36)^2 \\ 9926136900 &:= (99261 + 369 + 00)^2 \\ 9940688209 &:= (99406 + 88 + 209)^2 \\ 9980010000 &:= (99800 + 100 + 00)^2 \\ 9980209801 &:= (99802 + 098 + 01)^2 \\ 9989003025 &:= (99890 + 030 + 25)^2 \\ 9991002025 &:= (99910 + 020 + 25)^2 \\ 9998000100 &:= (99980 + 0010 + 0)^2 \\ 9998200081 &:= (99982 + 0008 + 1)^2 \\ 9999800001 &:= (99998 + 0000 + 1)^2 \\ 10999394884 &:= (1 + 09993 + 94884)^2 \\ 12519490248 &:= (125 + 1949 + 0248)^3 \\ 13769379649 &:= (1 + 37693 + 79649)^2 \\ 19902511000 &:= (199 + 02511 + 000)^3 \\ 20301732352 &:= (203 + 0173 + 2352)^3 \\ 29869171929 &:= (29 + 869 + 171929)^2 \\ 62416028224 &:= (6 + 241602 + 8224)^2 \\ 76024275625 &:= (76 + 024 + 275625)^2 \\ 93824221184 &:= (938 + 2422 + 1184)^3 \end{aligned}$$

4.2.2 Positive and Negative Signs

$$196 := (-1 + 9 + 6)^2$$

$$243 := (2 + 4 - 3)^5$$

$$512 := (5 - 1 - 2)^9$$

$$1024 := (10 - 2 - 4)^5$$

$$1331 := (13 - 3 + 1)^3$$

$$1936 := (-1 + 9 + 36)^2$$

$$2048 := (-2 - 04 + 8)^{11}$$

$$3364 := (-3 - 3 + 64)^2$$

$$3969 := (3 - 9 + 69)^2$$

$$5776 := (5 + 77 - 6)^2$$

$$7396 := (-7 - 3 + 96)^2$$

$$11881 := (118 - 8 - 1)^2$$

$$12996 := (129 - 9 - 6)^2$$

$$15129 := (-1 - 5 + 129)^2$$

$$17161 := (-1 + 71 + 61)^2$$

$$17956 := (-1 + 79 + 56)^2$$

$$39204 := (3 - 9 + 204)^2$$

$$46225 := (-4 - 6 + 225)^2$$

$$46656 := (-4 + 66 - 56)^6$$

$$97336 := (9 + 73 - 36)^3$$

$$104329 := (-10 + 4 + 329)^2$$

$$161051 := (1 + 61 - 051)^5$$

$$195112 := (19 + 51 - 12)^3$$

$$300763 := (-3 + 007 + 63)^3$$

$$326041 := (-32 + 604 - 1)^2$$

$$456533 := (45 + 65 - 33)^3$$

$$608400 := (-60 + 840 + 0)^2$$

$$636056 := (-6 + 36 + 056)^3$$

$$678976 := (-67 + 897 - 6)^2$$

$$680625 := (-6 + 806 + 25)^2$$

$$790321 := (7 + 903 - 21)^2$$

$$808201 := (80 + 820 - 1)^2$$

$$829921 := (-82 + 992 + 1)^2$$

$$853776 := (853 + 77 - 6)^2$$

$$877969 := (877 - 9 + 69)^2$$

$$978121 := (978 + 12 - 1)^2$$

$$1018081 := (1018 - 08 - 1)^2$$

$$1020100 := (1020 - 10 + 0)^2$$

$$1022121 := (1022 - 12 + 1)^2$$

$$1030301 := (103 - 03 + 01)^3$$

$$1061208 := (106 - 12 + 08)^3$$

$$1089936 := (1089 - 9 - 36)^2$$

$$1179396 := (1179 + 3 - 96)^2$$

$$1229881 := (-1 + 229 + 881)^2$$

$$1229881 := (122 + 988 - 1)^2$$

$$1261129 := (-12 + 6 + 1129)^2$$

$$1336336 := (133 - 63 - 36)^4$$

$$1495729 := (-1 + 495 + 729)^2$$

$$1771561 := (-1 + 771 + 561)^2$$

$$1779556 := (-1 + 779 + 556)^2$$

$$3017169 := (30 + 1716 - 9)^2$$

$$3751969 := (-37 + 5 + 1969)^2$$

$$4084101 := (4 - 084 + 101)^5$$

$$4826809 := (-4 + 826 - 809)^6$$

$$7828804 := (-78 + 2880 - 4)^2$$

$$9129329 := (9 - 129 + 329)^3$$

$$9129329 := (-91 - 29 + 329)^3$$

$$10316944 := (-1 + 03169 + 44)^2$$

$$10793861 := (1079 + 3 - 861)^3$$

$$12326391 := (-123 + 263 + 91)^3$$

$$12355225 := (-12 + 3552 - 25)^2$$

$$14526784 := (-14 - 526 + 784)^3$$

$$20570824 := (20 - 570 + 824)^3$$

$$21594609 := (-21 + 59 + 4609)^2$$

$$23149125 := (-231 + 491 + 25)^3$$

$$23393656 := (23 - 393 + 656)^3$$

$$23639903 := (23 - 639 + 903)^3$$

$$24492601 := (24 + 4926 - 01)^2$$

$$28665316 := (-28 + 66 + 5316)^2$$

$$35153041 := (-35 + 153 - 041)^4$$

$$35426304 := (-354 + 2 + 6304)^2$$

$$35831808 := (35 - 831 + 808)^7$$

$$35916049 := (35 - 91 + 6049)^2$$

$$36857041 := (368 + 5704 - 1)^2$$

$$37015056 := (37 - 015 + 056)^4$$

$$39135393 := (391 + 35 - 393)^5$$

$$41216400 := (41 - 21 + 6400)^2$$

$$43243551 := (43 - 243 + 551)^3$$

$$43986977 := (-439 + 869 - 77)^3$$

$$43996689 := (43 - 99 + 6689)^2$$

$$45435424 := (45 - 435 + 424)^5$$

$$46063369 := (460 + 6336 - 9)^2$$

$$46977316 := (-469 + 7 + 7316)^2$$

$$47073321 := (-470 + 7332 - 1)^2$$

$$47832147 := (478 + 32 - 147)^3$$

$$48228544 := (48 - 228 + 544)^3$$

$$48566961 := (-48 + 56 + 6961)^2$$

$$52867441 := (528 + 6744 - 1)^2$$

$$54010152 := (540 - 10 - 152)^3$$

$$54745201 := (-54 + 7452 + 01)^2$$

$$57927321 := (5 + 7927 - 321)^2$$

$$66080641 := (66 + 08064 - 1)^2$$

$$76895361 := (-768 + 9536 + 1)^2$$

$$78402752 := (78 - 402 + 752)^3$$

$$79049881 := (7904 + 988 - 1)^2$$

$$80910025 := (-80 + 9100 - 25)^2$$

$$82828201 := (8282 + 820 - 1)^2$$

$$90973444 := (9097 - 3 + 444)^2$$

$$91795561 := (9 + 17 + 9556 - 1)^2$$

$$91968100 := (-91 + 9681 + 00)^2$$

$$96079204 := (-9 + 607 + 9204)^2$$

$$96079204 := (9607 - 9 + 204)^2$$

$$98446084 := (9844 - 6 + 084)^2$$

$$99780121 := (9978 + 012 - 1)^2$$

$$100020001 := (10002 + 000 - 1)^2$$

$$100180081 := (10018 - 008 - 1)^2$$

$$100200100 := (10020 - 010 + 0)^2$$

$$100220121 := (10022 - 012 + 1)^2$$

$$100902025 := (10090 - 20 - 25)^2$$

$$101103025 := (10110 - 30 - 25)^2$$

$$101566084 := (10156 + 6 - 084)^2$$

$$101989801 := (10198 - 98 - 01)^2$$

$$102475129 := (10247 + 5 - 129)^2$$

$$102637161 := (10263 - 71 - 61)^2$$

$$102697956 := (10269 - 79 - 56)^2$$

$$104346225 := (10434 + 6 - 225)^2$$

$$105413504 := (105 + 413 - 504)^7$$

$$106564329 := (10656 - 4 - 329)^2$$

$$111746041 := (11174 - 604 + 1)^2$$

$$116208400 := (11620 - 840 + 0)^2$$

$$117158976 := (11715 - 897 + 6)^2$$

$$119049921 := (11904 - 992 - 1)^2$$

$$130323843 := (-13 - 0323 + 843)^3$$

$$132618256 := (-1 + 3261 + 8256)^2$$

$$133432831 := (-1 + 3343 - 2831)^3$$

$$139617856 := (-1 + 3961 + 7856)^2$$

$$177715561 := (-1 + 7771 + 5561)^2$$

$$177795556 := (-1 + 7779 + 5556)^2$$

$$180714249 := (1 - 807 + 14249)^2$$

$$188132517 := (188 - 132 + 517)^3$$

$$244015641 := (-24 + 4 + 015641)^2$$

$$258474853 := (258 - 474 + 853)^3$$

$$312900721 := (312 - 900 + 721)^4$$

$$352275361 := (3 - 5227 + 5361)^4$$

$$360944128 := (-360 + 944 + 128)^3$$

$$363994344 := (-3639 + 9 + 4344)^3$$

$$365525875 := (365 - 525 + 875)^3$$

$$384240583 := (384 - 240 + 583)^3$$

$$429981696 := (429 - 981 + 696)^4$$

$$504358336 := (-5043 + 5833 + 6)^3$$

$$\begin{aligned} 547981281 &:= (-547 + 981 - 281)^4 \\ 605495736 &:= (605 - 495 + 736)^3 \\ 609800192 &:= (60 + 980 - 0192)^3 \\ 783777448 &:= (-7 + 8377 - 7448)^3 \\ 786330467 &:= (786 - 330 + 467)^3 \\ 876929769 &:= (-87 - 69 + 29769)^2 \\ \\ 1003003001 &:= (1003 - 003 + 001)^3 \\ 1006012008 &:= (1006 - 012 + 008)^3 \\ 1252726552 &:= (1252 - 726 + 552)^3 \\ 1256216039 &:= (1256 - 216 + 039)^3 \\ 1261599361 &:= (-1 + 26159 + 9361)^2 \\ 1305015625 &:= (-1 + 30501 + 5625)^2 \\ 1312932375 &:= (13 - 1293 + 2375)^3 \\ 1316532736 &:= (13 - 1653 + 2736)^3 \\ 1441037521 &:= (-1 + 441 + 037521)^2 \\ 1456338244 &:= (-145 + 63 + 38244)^2 \\ 1543939849 &:= (-154 + 39398 + 49)^2 \\ 1544804416 &:= (1544 - 804 + 416)^3 \\ 1549839424 &:= (-154 + 98 + 39424)^2 \\ 1566338929 &:= (-15 + 663 + 38929)^2 \\ 1771561000 &:= (1771 - 561 + 000)^3 \\ 2242496025 &:= (-2242 + 49602 - 5)^2 \\ 2355452089 &:= (-2 - 3554 + 52089)^2 \\ 2426449081 &:= (242 - 64 + 49081)^2 \\ 2649057961 &:= (-2 - 6490 + 57961)^2 \\ 2655134784 &:= (265 + 51347 - 84)^2 \\ 2779431416 &:= (2779 + 43 - 1416)^3 \\ 2822053129 &:= (-28 + 22 + 053129)^2 \\ 3029952025 &:= (3029 - 9 + 52025)^2 \\ 3651059776 &:= (-3 + 651 + 059776)^2 \\ 3666512088 &:= (-3666 + 5120 + 88)^3 \\ 4125364441 &:= (41 - 253 + 64441)^2 \\ 5171911056 &:= (-51 + 71911 + 056)^2 \\ 5186700891 &:= (-5186 + 7008 - 91)^3 \\ 5574115600 &:= (-55 + 74115 + 600)^2 \\ 6390083844 &:= (-6 - 3900 + 83844)^2 \\ 6597500625 &:= (-65 + 975 - 00625)^4 \\ \\ 6860643241 &:= (6 + 86064 - 3241)^2 \\ 6891541327 &:= (689 + 1541 - 327)^3 \\ 6978430369 &:= (-697 + 84303 - 69)^2 \\ 8118190201 &:= (81 - 181 + 90201)^2 \\ 8230172859 &:= (-823 - 017 + 2859)^3 \\ 8598667441 &:= (85986 + 6744 - 1)^2 \\ 8688663369 &:= (86886 + 6336 - 9)^2 \\ 8822657041 &:= (88226 + 5704 - 1)^2 \\ 9109557136 &:= (-91 + 095571 - 36)^2 \\ 9228868489 &:= (9228 + 86848 - 9)^2 \\ 9655617169 &:= (96556 + 1716 - 9)^2 \\ 9822990321 &:= (98229 + 903 - 21)^2 \\ 9942682369 &:= (99426 - 82 + 369)^2 \\ 9979810201 &:= (99798 + 102 - 01)^2 \\ 9984406084 &:= (99844 - 06 + 084)^2 \\ 9997800121 &:= (99978 + 0012 - 1)^2 \\ \\ 10057482369 &:= (100574 + 82 - 369)^2 \\ 10059488209 &:= (100594 - 88 - 209)^2 \\ 10391151969 &:= (103911 - 5 - 1969)^2 \\ 10517853871 &:= (105 - 1785 + 3871)^3 \\ 10567428804 &:= (105674 - 2880 + 4)^2 \\ 10671096601 &:= (-10 + 6710 + 96601)^2 \\ 11012193721 &:= (-1 + 101219 + 3721)^2 \\ 11033611681 &:= (-1 + 103361 + 1681)^2 \\ 11225826304 &:= (112258 - 2 - 6304)^2 \\ 11284642907 &:= (-1128 + 464 + 2907)^3 \\ 11417777316 &:= (114177 - 7 - 7316)^2 \\ 11419273321 &:= (114192 - 7332 + 1)^2 \\ 11830695361 &:= (118306 - 9536 - 1)^2 \\ 13141183225 &:= (-1 + 31411 + 83225)^2 \\ 13413413376 &:= (-1341 + 341 + 3376)^3 \\ 16620420608 &:= (-1662 + 04206 + 08)^3 \\ 17777155561 &:= (-1 + 77771 + 55561)^2 \\ 17777955556 &:= (-1 + 77779 + 55556)^2 \\ 18454135716 &:= (184 - 54 + 135716)^2 \\ 30900024072 &:= (3090 - 0024 + 072)^3 \\ 33061785241 &:= (3306 + 178524 - 1)^2 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 39922038025 &:= (-3992 + 203802 - 5)^2 \\ 39993200289 &:= (-399 + 93 + 200289)^2 \\ 40071907448 &:= (-4007 - 19 + 07448)^3 \\ 42082009321 &:= (4208 + 200932 - 1)^2 \\ 72162614161 &:= (7216 + 261416 - 1)^2 \\ 77127842961 &:= (-771 + 278429 + 61)^2 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 78242718961 &:= (7824 + 271896 - 1)^2 \\ 91819302289 &:= (-91 + 819 + 302289)^2 \\ 98265321729 &:= (9 - 8265 + 321729)^2 \\ 99747325584 &:= (-9 - 9747 + 325584)^2 \end{aligned}$$

5 Numbers with Different Powers

This section brings **semi-selfie numbers** in such a way that same number can be written in different powers

$$\begin{aligned} 1296 &:= (1 + 2 + 9 - 6)^4 & & := (10 - 4 + 8 + 5 + 7 + 6)^4 \\ &:= (1 + 29 + 6)^2 & & \\ 10000 &:= (10 + 000)^4 & & := (16 + 7 - 9 + 6 + 16)^8 \\ &:= (100 + 00)^2 & & := (1 + 679 + 616)^2 \\ 15625 &:= (1 + 5 + 6 - 2 - 5)^6 & & := (177 - 1 - 56 + 1)^3 \\ &:= (1 + 5 - 6 + 25)^3 & & \\ 16384 &:= (1 - 6 + 3 + 8 - 4)^{14} & & := (-1 + 771 + 561)^2 \\ &:= (1 - 6 - 3 + 8 + 4)^7 & & \\ 19683 &:= (1 - 9 + 6 + 8 - 3)^9 & & := (19 - 5 - 3 + 1 - 2 - 5)^9 \\ &:= (1 + 9 + 6 + 8 + 3)^3 & & := (1 + 95 + 3 + 1 + 25)^3 \\ 32768 &:= (-3 - 2 - 7 + 6 + 8)^{15} & & := (20 - 9 - 7 + 1 - 5 + 2)^{21} \\ &:= (3 - 2 - 7 + 6 + 8)^5 & & := (20 - 9 - 7 + 1 + 5 - 2)^7 \\ &:= (3 + 27 - 6 + 8)^3 & & := (-20 + 97 - 1 + 52)^3 \\ 262144 &:= (2 - 6 - 2 + 14 - 4)^9 & & := (29 + 8 + 5 + 98 + 4)^3 \\ &:= (2 - 6 + 2 + 14 - 4)^6 & & \\ 390625 &:= (-3 + 9 + 0 + 6 - 2 - 5)^8 & & := (41 - 9 + 4 - 30 - 4)^{22} \\ &:= (3 - 9 + 0 + 6 + 25)^4 & & := (-4 + 19 - 4 - 3 + 0 - 4)^{11} \\ 531441 &:= (-5 - 3 + 14 - 4 + 1)^{12} & & := (4 - 7 - 8 + 2 + 9 - 6 + 9)^{14} \\ &:= (53 + 1 - 4 - 41)^6 & & := (4 + 7 + 8 + 2 - 9 + 6 - 9)^7 \\ &:= (5 + 31 - 4 - 4 - 1)^4 & & \\ &:= (5 + 31 + 4 + 41)^3 & & \\ 1000000 &:= (10 + 00000)^6 & & := (-4 + 826 - 809)^6 \\ &:= (100 + 0000)^3 & & := (4 + 82 - 6 + 80 + 9)^3 \\ &:= (1000 + 000)^2 & & \\ 1048576 &:= (10 + 4 - 8 - 5 + 7 - 6)^{20} & & := (9 - 76 + 5 + 62 + 5)^{10} \\ &:= (10 + 4 + 8 - 5 - 7 - 6)^{10} & & := (-97 + 65 + 62 - 5)^5 \\ &:= (10 + 4 + 8 - 5 - 7 + 6)^5 & & \\ 10077696 &:= (1 + 007 + 7 + 6 - 9 - 6)^9 & & := (100 + 7 + 7 + 6 + 96)^3 \\ 14348907 &:= (14 + 3 - 4 - 8 - 9 + 07)^{15} & & \\ &:= (14 + 3 + 4 + 8 - 9 + 07)^5 & & \\ &:= (143 + 4 + 89 + 07)^3 & & \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 \mathbf{16777216} &:= (16 - 7 - 7 + 7 - 2 + 1 - 6)^{24} &:= (3 + 8 - 7 + 4 - 20 + 4 + 8 + 9)^9 \\
 &:= (16 + 7 - 7 - 7 + 2 - 1 - 6)^{12} &:= (3 + 8 - 7 + 4 - 20 + 48 - 9)^6 \\
 &:= (16 + 7 + 7 - 7 - 21 + 6)^8 &\mathbf{429981696} := (4 + 2 + 99 + 8 + 1 - 6 - 96)^8 \\
 &:= (16 + 7 - 7 + 7 - 2 + 1 - 6)^6 &:= (4 + 2 + 99 + 8 + 16 + 9 + 6)^4 \\
 &:= (16 + 7 + 7 + 7 + 21 + 6)^4 &\mathbf{481890304} := (4 - 81 + 8 + 90 + 3 + 04)^6 \\
 \mathbf{33554432} &:= (33 + 5 + 5 + 4 - 43 - 2)^{25} &:= (481 + 8 - 9 + 0304)^3 \\
 &:= (33 - 5 + 5 - 4 + 4 - 3 + 2)^5 &\mathbf{594823321} := (5 + 94 - 82 + 33 - 21)^6 \\
 \mathbf{34012224} &:= (34 - 012 + 2 - 2 - 4)^6 &:= (5 - 9 + 4 + 823 - 3 + 21)^3 \\
 &:= (340 - 12 + 2 - 2 - 4)^3 &\mathbf{815730721} := (81 - 57 + 3 + 07 - 21)^8 \\
 \mathbf{43046721} &:= (43 - 046 + 7 - 2 + 1)^{16} &:= (81 + 57 + 3 + 07 + 21)^4 \\
 &:= (4 + 30 + 46 - 72 + 1)^8 &\mathbf{887503681} := (88 - 7 - 5 + 036 - 81)^6 \\
 &:= (43 + 04 + 6 + 7 + 21)^4 &:= (8 + 875 + 03 - 6 + 81)^3 \\
 \mathbf{60466176} &:= (60 - 46 + 6 - 1 - 7 - 6)^{10} &\mathbf{100000000} := (10 + 00000000)^9 \\
 &:= (6 + 04 + 6 + 6 + 1 + 7 + 6)^5 &:= (1000 + 000000)^3 \\
 \mathbf{67108864} &:= (67 - 1 + 08 - 8 - 64)^{26} &\mathbf{1073741824} := (10 - 7 + 3 + 7 + 4 - 1 - 8 - 2 - 4)^{30} \\
 &:= (67 + 1 + 08 - 8 - 64)^{13} &:= (10 + 7 - 3 + 7 - 4 + 1 - 8 - 2 - 4)^{15} \\
 \mathbf{85766121} &:= (8 + 57 - 66 + 1 + 21)^6 &:= (10 + 7 - 3 + 7 - 4 + 1 - 8 + 2 - 4)^{10} \\
 &:= (-8 + 576 - 6 - 121)^3 &:= (10 + 7 + 3 + 7 + 4 - 1 + 8 - 2 - 4)^6 \\
 \mathbf{100000000} &:= (10 + 0000000)^8 &:= (10 + 7 + 3 - 7 + 41 + 8 - 2 + 4)^5 \\
 &:= (100 + 000000)^4 &\mathbf{1291467969} := (1 + 29 + 14 + 67 - 9 - 69)^6 \\
 &:= (10000 + 0000)^2 &:= (1 + 291 + 4 + 6 + 796 - 9)^3 \\
 \mathbf{134217728} &:= (1 - 3 + 42 - 17 + 7 - 28)^{27} &\mathbf{1475789056} := (147 + 5 + 7 - 89 - 056)^8 \\
 &:= (1 + 3 + 42 - 17 + 7 - 28)^9 &:= (147 + 5 + 78 - 90 + 56)^4 \\
 &:= (1 + 3 + 421 + 77 + 2 + 8)^3 &\mathbf{1544804416} := (1 + 5 + 448 - 04 - 416)^6 \\
 &:= (1 + 5 + 448 - 04 - 416)^3 &:= (1544 - 804 + 416)^3 \\
 \mathbf{214358881} &:= (2 + 14 - 3 + 5 - 88 + 81)^8 &\mathbf{2176782336} := (21 + 76 - 78 + 23 - 36)^{12} \\
 &:= (214 - 3 + 5 - 8 - 88 + 1)^4 &:= (21 - 76 + 78 - 23 + 36)^6 \\
 &:= (214 - 3 + 5 - 8 - 88 + 1)^4 &:= (21 + 7 + 67 + 82 + 3 + 36)^4 \\
 &:= (2 - 4 - 4 + 140 - 6 + 2 - 5)^4 &:= (2 + 176 + 782 + 336)^3 \\
 \mathbf{268435456} &:= (2 - 68 - 4 + 3 + 5 + 4 + 56)^{28} &\mathbf{2562890625} := (2 + 56 + 28 - 90 - 6 + 25)^8 \\
 &:= (2 + 68 - 4 + 3 - 5 - 4 - 56)^{14} &:= (2 + 5 + 62 + 89 + 062 + 5)^4 \\
 &:= (2 + 68 - 4 - 3 + 5 + 4 - 56)^7 &\mathbf{3486784401} := (3 - 48 + 6 + 7 - 8 + 4 + 40 - 1)^{20} \\
 &:= (2 + 68 + 4 - 3 + 5 - 4 + 56)^4 &:= (3 + 48 - 6 - 7 + 8 + 4 - 40 - 1)^{10} \\
 \mathbf{282475249} &:= (28 - 24 - 7 - 5 + 24 - 9)^{10} &:= (3 + 48 - 6 - 7 + 8 - 4 + 40 - 1)^5 \\
 &:= (28 + 24 + 7 + 5 - 24 + 9)^5 &:= (3 + 48 + 67 + 84 + 40 + 1)^4 \\
 \mathbf{308915776} &:= (30 + 8 + 9 - 15 + 7 - 7 - 6)^6 &\mathbf{3518743761} := (3 + 51 + 87 - 4 - 37 - 61)^6 \\
 &:= (3 + 089 + 1 + 577 + 6)^3 &:= (3 + 5 + 1 + 8 + 743 + 761)^3 \\
 \mathbf{387420489} &:= (3 + 8 + 7 + 4 + 20 - 48 + 9)^{18} &\mathbf{4294967296} := (42 + 9 - 4 - 9 - 6 - 7 - 29 + 6)^{32}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 &:= (42 - 9 - 4 + 9 - 6 + 7 - 29 - 6)^{16} \\
 &:= (42 + 9 - 4 - 9 + 6 + 7 - 29 - 6)^8 \\
 &:= (42 - 9 + 49 + 6 + 72 + 96)^4 \\
 \mathbf{6103515625} &:= (610 + 3 - 51 - 562 + 5)^{14} \\
 &:= (610 - 3 - 515 - 62 - 5)^7 \\
 \mathbf{6975757441} &:= (69 + 75 - 75 - 7 - 44 - 1)^8 \\
 &:= (6 + 9 + 7 + 5 - 757 + 441)^4 \\
 \mathbf{8589934592} &:= (8 + 58 - 99 - 3 + 45 - 9 + 2)^{33} \\
 &:= (8 + 58 - 99 + 3 + 45 - 9 + 2)^{11} \\
 \mathbf{1000000000} &:= (10 + 0000 + 0000 + 0)^{10} \\
 &:= (100 + 0000 + 0000)^5 \\
 &:= (100000 + 0000 + 0)^2 \\
 \mathbf{10460353203} &:= (1 + 04 - 6 + 03 + 5 - 3 + 2 - 03)^{21} \\
 &:= (10 + 4 - 60 + 35 - 3 + 20 - 3)^{21} \\
 &:= (10 - 46 + 03 + 53 - 20 + 3)^{21} \\
 &:= (1 + 04 - 6 + 03 + 5 + 3 + 20 - 3)^7 \\
 &:= (10 + 4 - 60 - 3 + 53 + 20 + 3)^7 \\
 &:= (10 - 4 + 6 + 035 + 3 - 20 - 3)^7 \\
 \mathbf{10779215329} &:= (1 + 077 - 9 - 2 - 1 - 5 - 3 - 2 - 9)^6 \\
 &:= (10 - 7 + 7 + 9 + 2 - 15 + 32 + 9)^6 \\
 &:= (107 + 7 - 92 + 1 + 53 - 29)^6 \\
 &:= (1 - 077 + 9 - 215 + 329)^6 \\
 &:= (-1 + 07 + 79 + 2153 - 29)^3 \\
 \mathbf{12230590464} &:= (1 + 2 - 2 + 30 + 59 - 046 + 4)^6 \\
 &:= (12 - 2 + 30 + 5 + 9 + 04 - 6 - 4)^6 \\
 &:= (122 - 3 + 05 - 90 + 4 + 6 + 4)^6 \\
 &:= (1 - 22 - 305 - 90 + 464)^6 \\
 &:= (-12 + 2305 + 9 + 04 - 6 + 4)^3 \\
 \mathbf{13841287201} &:= (1 + 3 - 84 + 1 + 2 + 87 - 2 - 01)^{12} \\
 &:= (13 - 84 - 12 + 87 + 2 + 01)^{12} \\
 &:= (138 - 41 - 2 - 87 - 2 + 01)^{12} \\
 &:= (1 + 3 + 8 + 4 + 1 + 28 + 7 - 2 - 01)^6 \\
 &:= (138 - 4 + 1 - 287 + 201)^6 \\
 &:= (13 - 84 + 128 - 7 - 2 + 01)^6 \\
 &:= (1 + 38 + 412 - 87 - 20 - 1)^4 \\
 &:= (13 + 8 + 412 - 87 - 2 - 01)^4 \\
 &:= (138 + 4 + 1 - 2 + 8 - 7 + 201)^4 \\
 \mathbf{15625000000} &:= (1 + 5 - 6 + 2500 + 0000)^3 \\
 &:= (1 + 56 - 2 - 5 + 0000 + 00)^6 \\
 &:= (1 - 5 + 6 - 2 + 50 + 00000)^6 \\
 \mathbf{16983563041} &:= (1 + 6 + 98 + 3 - 56 - 30 - 4 + 1)^8 \\
 &:= (16 + 9 + 8 + 3 + 5 - 63 + 041)^8 \\
 &:= (16 + 98 - 35 - 63 + 04 - 1)^8 \\
 &:= (169 - 83 - 56 + 30 - 41)^8 \\
 &:= (1 + 69 - 8 - 3 + 5 - 6 + 304 - 1)^4 \\
 &:= (16 + 983 - 5 - 630 - 4 + 1)^4 \\
 &:= (16 - 9 - 8 + 356 + 3 + 04 - 1)^4 \\
 \mathbf{17179869184} &:= (1 + 7 - 179 - 8 + 6 + 91 + 84)^{34} \\
 &:= (17 - 1 + 79 - 86 - 91 + 84)^{34} \\
 &:= (171 - 79 + 8 - 6 - 9 + 1 - 84)^{34} \\
 &:= (17 - 17 - 98 + 6 + 9 + 1 + 84)^{34} \\
 &:= (17 + 17 - 9 - 8 - 6 - 91 + 84)^{17} \\
 &:= (-171 - 7 - 9 - 8 + 6 + 9 + 184)^{17} \\
 &:= (171 - 79 - 8 - 6 + 9 + 1 - 84)^{17} \\
 \mathbf{25937424601} &:= (2 + 59 - 37 - 4 + 2 - 4 - 6 - 01)^{10} \\
 &:= (25 + 9 + 3 + 7 + 4 + 24 - 60 - 1)^{10} \\
 &:= (2 - 593 + 7 - 4 + 2 - 4 + 601)^{10} \\
 &:= (2 + 593 - 7 - 4 - 2 - 460 - 1)^5 \\
 &:= (25 + 9 - 374 + 2 + 460 - 1)^5 \\
 &:= (259 + 3 - 74 - 2 - 4 - 60 - 1)^5 \\
 &:= (2593 - 7 - 4 - 2460 - 1)^5 \\
 \mathbf{30517578125} &:= (3 + 05 + 1 + 7 + 5 - 7 + 8 - 12 - 5)^{15} \\
 &:= (30 + 5 + 17 + 5 - 78 + 1 + 25)^{15} \\
 &:= (3 - 051 - 7 - 57 - 8 + 125)^{15} \\
 &:= (30 + 5 + 175 - 78 - 12 + 5)^5 \\
 &:= (3 - 05 - 1 - 7 - 5 + 7 + 8 + 125)^5 \\
 &:= (305 - 17 - 57 - 81 - 25)^5 \\
 &:= (3051 + 7 + 57 + 8 - 1 - 2 + 5)^3 \\
 \mathbf{30840979456} &:= (3 + 084 + 09 - 79 + 45 - 6)^6 \\
 &:= (30 + 840 - 9 - 794 - 5 - 6)^6 \\
 &:= (308 - 409 + 7 + 94 + 56)^6 \\
 &:= (-30 + 8 + 4097 - 945 + 6)^3 \\
 \mathbf{31381059609} &:= (3 - 138 + 10 + 59 + 60 + 9)^{12} \\
 &:= (31 - 38 - 1 + 05 + 9 + 6 - 09)^{12} \\
 &:= (3 + 1 - 38 - 1 + 059 - 6 - 09)^{11} \\
 &:= (31 + 3 - 81 + 059 + 6 - 09)^{11}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 \mathbf{34359738368} &:= (3 + 43 + 5 + 9 - 73 + 83 - 68)^{35} \\
 &:= (3 - 4 + 359 + 7 - 3 + 8 - 368)^{35} \\
 &:= (34 + 35 - 9 - 73 + 83 - 68)^{35} \\
 &:= (34 - 35 + 97 + 3 - 83 - 6 - 8)^{35} \\
 &:= (34 + 35 - 97 + 3 - 8 - 3 + 68)^7 \\
 &:= (34 - 3 + 59 - 73 + 83 - 68)^7 \\
 &:= (343 + 59 - 738 + 368)^7 \\
 &:= (3 - 4 - 359 + 7 + 383 - 6 + 8)^7 \\
 &:= (3 + 4 - 3 - 5 + 973 - 836 - 8)^5 \\
 &:= (3 + 43 - 59 - 7 - 3 + 83 + 68)^5 \\
 &:= (-343 - 5 + 97 + 3 + 8 + 368)^5 \\
 &:= (34 - 35 + 973 - 836 - 8)^5 \\
 \mathbf{37822859361} &:= (3 + 7 + 8 + 22 + 8 + 5 - 93 + 61)^8 \\
 &:= (37 + 8 - 2 + 28 + 5 + 9 - 3 - 61)^8 \\
 &:= (378 + 2 - 2 + 8 + 5 - 9 - 361)^8 \\
 &:= (3 + 78 - 228 + 593 - 6 + 1)^4 \\
 &:= (378 + 2 + 2 + 85 + 9 - 36 + 1)^4 \\
 &:= (3 - 782 + 285 + 936 - 1)^4 \\
 \mathbf{38068692544} &:= (3 + 8 - 06 + 8 - 6 - 9 + 2 + 54 + 4)^6 \\
 &:= (3 - 80 + 686 - 9 + 2 - 544)^6 \\
 &:= (38 - 068 + 69 - 25 + 44)^6 \\
 &:= (3 + 806 + 8 - 6 + 9 + 2544)^3 \\
 \mathbf{38443359375} &:= (3 + 84 - 433 - 5 - 9 + 375)^9 \\
 &:= (38 + 4 + 4 + 335 + 9 - 375)^9 \\
 &:= (384 - 433 - 5 - 9 + 3 + 75)^9 \\
 &:= (3 + 8 + 4 - 4 + 3359 + 3 + 7 - 5)^3 \\
 \mathbf{42180533641} &:= (4 - 2 + 1 + 80 + 53 - 36 - 41)^6 \\
 &:= (42 + 1 - 8 - 053 + 36 + 41)^6 \\
 &:= (42 + 1 + 80 - 5 + 3364 - 1)^3 \\
 \mathbf{51520374361} &:= (51 + 5 - 20 - 37 + 4 - 3 + 61)^6 \\
 &:= (5 - 15 + 20 + 37 + 4 + 3 + 6 + 1)^6 \\
 &:= (515 + 20 - 37 - 436 - 1)^6 \\
 &:= (-5 + 1 - 5 - 20 + 3743 + 6 + 1)^3 \\
 \mathbf{54875873536} &:= (54 + 87 + 5 + 8 - 73 - 53 - 6)^8 \\
 &:= (54 + 87 - 5 + 8 - 7 + 353 - 6)^4 \\
 &:= (5 - 4 + 8 - 758 + 735 + 36)^8 \\
 &:= (548 + 75 + 8 - 73 - 536)^8 \\
 &:= (5 + 4 + 8 + 7 + 5 - 8 - 73 + 536)^4
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 &:= (548 + 7 + 5 - 87 + 3 + 5 - 3 + 6)^4 \\
 \mathbf{61917364224} &:= (6 + 19 - 173 - 64 + 224)^{10} \\
 &:= (619 + 1 + 7 + 3 - 642 + 24)^{10} \\
 &:= (61 - 91 + 7 + 3 + 6 + 4 - 2 + 24)^{10} \\
 &:= (61 + 9 + 17 - 3 - 6 + 42 + 24)^5 \\
 &:= (619 + 173 - 642 - 2 - 4)^5 \\
 &:= (61 - 9 - 1 + 73 - 6 + 4 - 2 + 24)^5 \\
 &:= (6 - 1 - 91 - 7 + 3 + 6 + 4 + 224)^5 \\
 \mathbf{68719476736} &:= (6 + 87 + 1 + 9 + 4 - 76 + 7 - 36)^{36} \\
 &:= (687 + 1 + 9 + 47 - 6 - 736)^{36} \\
 &:= (68 - 71 - 9 - 47 - 6 + 73 - 6)^{36} \\
 &:= (6 + 87 - 194 + 76 - 7 + 36)^{18} \\
 &:= (68 + 7 + 1 + 9 - 4 - 7 - 67 + 3 - 6)^{18} \\
 &:= (687 - 19 - 4 + 76 - 736)^{18} \\
 \mathbf{68719476736} &:= (6 + 8 - 7 - 19 + 4 - 7 - 6 - 7 + 36)^{12} \\
 &:= (6 + 87 - 1 - 9 - 4 - 7 - 67 - 3 + 6)^{12} \\
 &:= (68 - 71 - 94 + 76 - 7 + 36)^{12} \\
 &:= (6 + 87 + 1 - 9 - 47 - 6 - 7 - 3 - 6)^9 \\
 &:= (68 + 7 + 19 - 47 - 67 + 36)^9 \\
 &:= (687 + 19 - 4 - 7 - 673 - 6)^9 \\
 \mathbf{68719476736} &:= (6 + 87 + 19 - 4 - 7 + 6 - 7 - 36)^6 \\
 &:= (68 + 7 + 1 - 9 - 4 - 7 + 6 - 7 + 3 + 6)^6 \\
 &:= (68 + 71 + 9 - 47 + 6 - 7 - 36)^6 \\
 &:= (6 + 87 + 1 + 9 + 476 - 73 + 6)^4 \\
 &:= (68 + 7 - 1 - 9 + 476 + 7 - 36)^4 \\
 &:= (687 - 1 - 94 - 7 + 6 - 73 - 6)^4 \\
 &:= (-687 + 19 + 4767 + 3 - 6)^3 \\
 \mathbf{78310985281} &:= (7 + 8 + 31 + 09 - 8 + 5 - 28 - 1)^8 \\
 &:= (78 - 31 - 098 - 5 - 2 + 81)^8 \\
 &:= (7 + 8 + 3 + 1 - 09 - 8 + 528 - 1)^4 \\
 &:= (7 + 83 + 10 - 98 + 528 - 1)^4 \\
 &:= (78 + 310 + 98 + 52 - 8 - 1)^4 \\
 \mathbf{78364164096} &:= (7 - 83 - 6 + 4 - 16 + 4 + 096)^{14} \\
 &:= (78 - 36 - 41 + 6 - 4 + 09 - 6)^{14} \\
 &:= (7 - 8 + 36 + 416 - 409 - 6)^7 \\
 &:= (78 - 3 + 6 - 4 - 16 - 40 + 9 + 6)^7 \\
 &:= (783 - 641 - 6 - 4 - 096)^7
 \end{aligned}$$

6 Equalities: Positive and Positive-Negative Signs

This section brings numbers in such a way that one side we have numbers with positive sign and another side with positive and negative signs. In some cases, there are more than one possibility. The results are up to 11 digits:

$$\mathbf{512} := (5 + 1 + 2)^3 = (5 - 1 - 2)^9$$

$$\mathbf{1296} := (1 + 29 + 6)^2 = (1 + 2 + 9 - 6)^4$$

$$\mathbf{19683} := (1 + 9 + 6 + 8 + 3)^3 = (-1 + 9 + 6 - 8 - 3)^9$$

$$\mathbf{234256} := (2 + 3 + 4 + 2 + 5 + 6)^4 = (-234 + 256)^4$$

$$\mathbf{357911} := (3 + 57 + 9 + 1 + 1)^3 = (-3 - 5 + 79 + 1 - 1)^3$$

$$\mathbf{373248} := (37 + 3 + 24 + 8)^3 = (-3 + 73 - 2 - 4 + 8)^3$$

$$\mathbf{390625} := (3 + 9 + 06 + 2 + 5)^4 = (-3 + 9 - 06 + 25)^4$$

$$\mathbf{531441} := (5 + 31 + 4 + 41)^3$$

$$:= (5 + 3 + 14 + 4 + 1)^4 = (5 + 31 - 4 - 4 - 1)^4$$

$$= (53 - 1 - 44 + 1)^6$$

$$= (-5 - 3 + 14 - 4 + 1)^{12}$$

$$\mathbf{551368} := (55 + 13 + 6 + 8)^3 = (55 - 1 + 36 - 8)^3$$

$$\mathbf{614656} := (6 + 1 + 4 + 6 + 5 + 6)^4 = (-6 - 1 + 46 - 5 - 6)^4$$

$$\mathbf{970299} := (9 + 70 + 2 + 9 + 9)^3 = (9 + 70 + 29 - 9)^3$$

$$\mathbf{1259712} := (1 + 25 + 9 + 71 + 2)^3 = (125 - 9 - 7 + 1 - 2)^3$$

$$\mathbf{1336336} := (13 + 3 + 6 + 3 + 3 + 6)^4 = (133 - 63 - 36)^4$$

$$\mathbf{1679616} := (1 + 6 + 7 + 9 + 6 + 1 + 6)^4 = (1 + 6 + 7 - 9 + 6 + 1 - 6)^8$$

$$\mathbf{1679616} := (1 + 679 + 616)^2 = (16 + 7 - 9 + 6 + 16)^4$$

$$\mathbf{1874161} := (18 + 7 + 4 + 1 + 6 + 1)^4 = (-18 + 7 + 41 + 6 + 1)^4$$

$$\mathbf{1953125} := (1 + 95 + 3 + 1 + 25)^3 = (1 - 9 + 5 + 3 + 125)^3$$

$$\mathbf{2515456} := (25 + 1 + 54 + 56)^3 = (-2 - 5 + 154 - 5 - 6)^3$$

$$\mathbf{2985984} := (29 + 8 + 5 + 98 + 4)^3 = (29 + 8 + 59 - 84)^6$$

$$\mathbf{3652264} := (36 + 52 + 2 + 64)^3 = (-3 - 65 + 226 - 4)^3$$

$$\mathbf{5929741} := (5 + 92 + 9 + 74 + 1)^3 = (-5 + 92 + 97 - 4 + 1)^3$$

$$\mathbf{6751269} := (67 + 51 + 2 + 69)^3 = (67 + 5 + 126 - 9)^3$$

$$\mathbf{7311616} := (7 + 31 + 1 + 6 + 1 + 6)^4 = (73 - 11 + 6 - 16)^4$$

$$\mathbf{8503056} := (8 + 5 + 030 + 5 + 6)^4 = (85 - 030 + 5 - 6)^4$$

$$\mathbf{9150625} := (9 + 15 + 06 + 25)^4 = (9 - 1 + 50 - 6 - 2 + 5)^4$$

$$\mathbf{11316496} := (1 + 1 + 31 + 6 + 4 + 9 + 6)^4 = (11 - 3 + 1 - 6 + 49 + 6)^4$$

$$\mathbf{13845841} := (1 + 38 + 4 + 5 + 8 + 4 + 1)^4 = (13 + 8 - 45 + 84 + 1)^4$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 \mathbf{14172488} &:= (14 + 172 + 48 + 8)^3 &= (-14 + 172 - 4 + 88)^3 \\
 \mathbf{14348907} &:= (143 + 4 + 89 + 07)^3 &= (14 + 3 + 4 + 8 - 9 + 07)^5 \\
 & &= (14 + 3 - 4 - 8 - 9 + 07)^{15} \\
 \mathbf{14526784} &:= (145 + 2 + 6 + 7 + 84)^3 &= (-14 - 526 + 784)^3 \\
 \mathbf{15752961} &:= (15 + 7 + 5 + 29 + 6 + 1)^4 &= (157 + 5 - 2 - 96 - 1)^4 \\
 \mathbf{16194277} &:= (161 + 9 + 4 + 2 + 77)^3 &= (161 + 94 - 2 + 7 - 7)^3 \\
 \mathbf{16777216} &:= (16 + 7 + 7 + 7 + 21 + 6)^4 &= (16 - 7 - 7 + 7 + 2 - 1 + 6)^6 \\
 & &= (16 - 7 + 7 + 7 - 21 + 6)^8 \\
 & &= (16 + 7 - 7 - 7 + 2 - 1 - 6)^{12} \\
 & &= (16 - 7 - 7 + 7 - 2 + 1 - 6)^{24} \\
 \\
 \mathbf{17210368} &:= (1 + 7 + 2 + 1 + 03 + 6 + 8)^5 &= (17 + 2 + 10 - 3 - 6 + 8)^5 \\
 \mathbf{17779581} &:= (1 + 77 + 7 + 95 + 81)^3 &= (177 + 7 - 9 + 5 + 81)^3 \\
 \mathbf{17984728} &:= (179 + 8 + 47 + 28)^3 &= (179 + 84 - 7 - 2 + 8)^3 \\
 \mathbf{20151121} &:= (20 + 15 + 11 + 21)^4 &= (-2 - 01 - 51 + 121)^4 \\
 \mathbf{21717639} &:= (217 + 17 + 6 + 39)^3 &= (217 + 1 + 7 + 63 - 9)^3 \\
 \mathbf{23639903} &:= (236 + 39 + 9 + 03)^3 &= (23 - 639 + 903)^3 \\
 \mathbf{26873856} &:= (2 + 6 + 8 + 7 + 38 + 5 + 6)^4 &= (26 - 8 - 7 - 3 + 8 + 56)^4 \\
 \mathbf{28372625} &:= (283 + 7 + 2 + 6 + 2 + 5)^3 &= (283 - 7 + 26 - 2 + 5)^3 \\
 \mathbf{28398241} &:= (28 + 3 + 9 + 8 + 24 + 1)^4 &= (28 + 3 - 9 + 8 + 2 + 41)^4 \\
 \mathbf{33362176} &:= (33 + 3 + 6 + 21 + 7 + 6)^4 &= (33 - 36 + 2 + 1 + 76)^4 \\
 \mathbf{34012224} &:= (3 + 4 + 01 + 2 + 2 + 2 + 4)^6 &= (340 - 12 - 2 + 2 - 4)^3 \\
 \mathbf{34328125} &:= (34 + 3 + 281 + 2 + 5)^3 &= (343 - 2 + 8 + 1 - 25)^3 \\
 \mathbf{43046721} &:= (43 + 04 + 6 + 7 + 21)^4 &= (43 - 046 + 7 - 2 + 1)^{16} \\
 \mathbf{45212176} &:= (45 + 21 + 2 + 1 + 7 + 6)^4 &= (-4 - 5 + 2 + 12 + 1 + 76)^4 \\
 \mathbf{46268279} &:= (46 + 26 + 8 + 279)^3 &= (4 + 626 + 8 - 279)^3 \\
 \mathbf{52521875} &:= (5 + 2 + 5 + 2 + 1 + 8 + 7 + 5)^5 &= (5 + 25 + 2 - 1 - 8 + 7 + 5)^5 \\
 \mathbf{60466176} &:= (6 + 04 + 6 + 6 + 1 + 7 + 6)^5 &= (60 - 46 - 6 - 1 - 7 + 6)^{10} \\
 \mathbf{63297936} &:= (6 + 3 + 2 + 9 + 7936)^2 &= (-6 - 3 + 29 + 7936)^2 \\
 \mathbf{68574961} &:= (6 + 8 + 57 + 4 + 9 + 6 + 1)^4 &= (6 - 8 - 5 + 7 - 4 + 96 - 1)^4 \\
 \\
 \mathbf{108531333} &:= (108 + 5 + 31 + 333)^3 &= (-10 - 8 + 531 - 33 - 3)^3 \\
 \mathbf{112550881} &:= (11 + 25 + 50 + 8 + 8 + 1)^4 &= (112 - 5 - 5 - 08 + 8 + 1)^4 \\
 \mathbf{126247696} &:= (12 + 62 + 4 + 7 + 6 + 9 + 6)^4 &= (126 - 24 + 7 - 6 + 9 - 6)^4 \\
 \mathbf{134217728} &:= (1 + 3 + 421 + 7 + 72 + 8)^3 &= (134 - 21 - 77 - 28)^9 \\
 \mathbf{136048896} &:= (13 + 60 + 4 + 8 + 8 + 9 + 6)^4 &= (13 + 60 - 48 + 89 - 6)^4 \\
 \mathbf{141158161} &:= (14 + 1 + 1 + 5 + 81 + 6 + 1)^4 &= (14 + 115 - 81 + 61)^4 \\
 \mathbf{157351936} &:= (15 + 7 + 35 + 19 + 36)^4 &= (157 - 35 - 19 + 3 + 6)^4 \\
 \mathbf{158340421} &:= (158 + 340 + 42 + 1)^3 &= (1 + 583 - 40 - 4 + 2 - 1)^3
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 164566592 &:= (16 + 456 + 65 + 9 + 2)^3 &= (-16 - 4 - 5 + 665 - 92)^3 \\ 164916224 &:= (16 + 4 + 9 + 1 + 6 + 2 + 2 + 4)^5 &= (16 + 49 - 1 + 6 - 2 - 24)^5 \\ 165469149 &:= (1 + 65 + 469 + 1 + 4 + 9)^3 &= (16 + 546 - 9 + 1 + 4 - 9)^3 \\ 174676879 &:= (1 + 7 + 467 + 68 + 7 + 9)^3 &= (1 + 7 + 467 + 6 + 87 - 9)^3 \\ 174900625 &:= (1 + 74 + 9 + 006 + 25)^4 &= (174 - 90 + 06 + 25)^4 \\ 184528125 &:= (18 + 4 + 5 + 2 + 8 + 1 + 2 + 5)^5 &= (18 - 45 - 2 + 81 - 2 - 5)^5 \\ 187388721 &:= (18 + 73 + 8 + 8 + 7 + 2 + 1)^4 &= (187 + 3 + 8 - 8 - 72 - 1)^4 \\ 193877776 &:= (1 + 9 + 3 + 8 + 77 + 7 + 7 + 6)^4 &= (193 + 8 - 7 - 77 + 7 - 6)^4 \\ 205962976 &:= (2 + 05 + 9 + 6 + 2 + 9 + 7 + 6)^5 &= (20 - 5 - 9 + 62 - 9 - 7 - 6)^5 \\ 214358881 &:= (2 + 1 + 43 + 58 + 8 + 8 + 1)^4 &= (214 - 3 + 5 - 8 - 88 + 1)^4 \\ 219256227 &:= (21 + 9 + 2 + 562 + 2 + 7)^3 &= (21 - 9 + 2 + 562 + 27)^3 \\ 236421376 &:= (23 + 6 + 4 + 2 + 13 + 76)^4 &= (2 - 3 - 6 + 42 + 13 + 76)^4 \\ 251239591 &:= (25 + 1 + 2 + 3 + 9 + 591)^3 &= (25 + 1 + 23 - 9 + 591)^3 \\ 260144641 &:= (26 + 014 + 46 + 41)^4 &= (260 - 144 + 6 + 4 + 1)^4 \\ 273359449 &:= (273 + 359 + 4 + 4 + 9)^3 &= (27 + 33 + 594 + 4 - 9)^3 \\ 307546875 &:= (30 + 7 + 546 + 87 + 5)^3 &= (30 + 7 - 54 + 687 + 5)^3 \\ 308915776 &:= (3 + 089 + 1 + 577 + 6)^3 &= (-308 + 915 - 7 + 76)^3 \\ 312900721 &:= (31 + 29 + 0072 + 1)^4 &= (312 - 900 + 721)^4 \\ 332150625 &:= (33 + 21 + 50 + 6 + 25)^4 &= (3 - 3 - 2 + 150 - 6 - 2 - 5)^4 \\ 385828352 &:= (385 + 8 + 283 + 52)^3 &= (3 + 858 + 2 - 83 - 52)^3 \\ 406586896 &:= (40 + 6 + 5 + 8 + 68 + 9 + 6)^4 &= (40 + 6 + 5 + 86 + 8 - 9 + 6)^4 \\ 416832723 &:= (4 + 1 + 6 + 8 + 3 + 2 + 723)^3 &= (-4 + 1 + 683 - 2 + 72 - 3)^3 \\ 418195493 &:= (4 + 18 + 1 + 9 + 5 + 4 + 9 + 3)^5 &= (4 + 1 + 81 + 9 - 54 + 9 + 3)^5 \\ 429981696 &:= (4 + 2 + 9 + 98 + 16 + 9 + 6)^4 &= (4 + 2 + 9 + 98 + 1 - 6 - 96)^8 \\ 442050625 &:= (44 + 20 + 50 + 6 + 25)^4 &= (-4 + 42 + 050 + 62 - 5)^4 \\ 447697125 &:= (44 + 7 + 697 + 12 + 5)^3 &= (44 + 7 + 6 - 9 + 712 + 5)^3 \\ 459165024 &:= (4 + 5 + 9 + 1 + 6 + 5 + 024)^5 &= (45 - 9 + 1 + 6 + 5 + 02 + 4)^5 \\ 479785216 &:= (47 + 9 + 78 + 5 + 2 + 1 + 6)^4 &= (47 + 97 + 8 + 5 - 2 - 1 - 6)^4 \\ 480048687 &:= (48 + 0048 + 687)^3 &= (4 + 800 - 4 - 8 + 6 - 8 - 7)^3 \\ 494913671 &:= (4 + 94 + 9 + 13 + 671)^3 &= (-49 + 4 + 913 - 6 - 71)^3 \\ 498677257 &:= (49 + 8 + 677 + 2 + 57)^3 &= (-49 + 867 + 7 - 25 - 7)^3 \\ 503284375 &:= (5 + 03 + 28 + 4 + 3 + 7 + 5)^5 &= (50 - 3 - 28 + 4 + 37 - 5)^5 \\ 547981281 &:= (5 + 47 + 9 + 81 + 2 + 8 + 1)^4 &= (5 + 47 + 98 + 12 - 8 - 1)^4 \\ 549353259 &:= (549 + 3 + 5 + 3 + 259)^3 &= (5 + 493 + 5 + 325 - 9)^3 \\ 551368000 &:= (5 + 5 + 1 + 3 + 6 + 800 + 0)^3 &= (55 + 1 - 36 + 800 + 0)^3 \\ 562448656 &:= (56 + 24 + 4 + 8 + 6 + 56)^4 &= (5 + 624 - 486 + 5 + 6)^4 \\ 569722789 &:= (5 + 6 + 9 + 722 + 78 + 9)^3 &= (569 - 7 - 2 + 278 - 9)^3 \\ 584277056 &:= (5 + 8 + 42 + 770 + 5 + 6)^3 &= (5 + 842 - 7 + 7 - 05 - 6)^3 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 \mathbf{586376253} &:= (58 + 6 + 3 + 762 + 5 + 3)^3 &= (586 - 3 + 7 - 6 + 253)^3 \\
 \mathbf{588480472} &:= (5 + 8 + 8 + 4 + 804 + 7 + 2)^3 &= (58 + 848 + 04 - 72)^3 \\
 \mathbf{605495736} &:= (6 + 05 + 4 + 95 + 736)^3 &= (605 - 495 + 736)^3 \\
 \mathbf{607573201} &:= (60 + 7 + 57 + 32 + 01)^4 &= (-60 + 7 + 5 + 7 - 3 + 201)^4 \\
 \mathbf{612220032} &:= (6 + 1 + 2 + 2 + 2 + 003 + 2)^7 &= (6 + 1 - 2 - 2 + 20 - 03 - 2)^7 \\
 \mathbf{663054848} &:= (6 + 6 + 3 + 05 + 4 + 848)^3 &= (6 - 6 - 30 + 54 + 848)^3 \\
 \mathbf{683797841} &:= (683 + 79 + 78 + 41)^3 &= (68 + 37 - 9 + 784 + 1)^3 \\
 \mathbf{688465387} &:= (6 + 8 + 846 + 5 + 3 + 8 + 7)^3 &= (6 + 884 + 6 + 5 - 3 - 8 - 7)^3 \\
 \mathbf{688747536} &:= (6 + 88 + 7 + 47 + 5 + 3 + 6)^4 &= (688 + 7 - 4 + 7 - 536)^4 \\
 \mathbf{705911761} &:= (70 + 5 + 9 + 11 + 7 + 61)^4 &= (70 + 5 + 91 - 1 - 7 + 6 - 1)^4 \\
 \mathbf{709732288} &:= (709 + 73 + 22 + 88)^3 &= (7 + 0973 - 2 + 2 - 88)^3 \\
 \mathbf{726572699} &:= (7 + 2 + 65 + 726 + 99)^3 &= (7 + 265 - 72 + 699)^3 \\
 \mathbf{753571000} &:= (753 + 57 + 100 + 0)^3 &= (-75 - 3 - 5 - 7 + 1000)^3 \\
 \mathbf{759333136} &:= (7 + 59 + 33 + 31 + 36)^4 &= (75 - 9 + 33 + 31 + 36)^4 \\
 \mathbf{799178752} &:= (79 + 9 + 1 + 787 + 52)^3 &= (7 - 9 + 91 + 787 + 52)^3 \\
 \mathbf{815730721} &:= (81 + 57 + 3 + 07 + 21)^4 &= (81 - 57 + 3 + 07 - 21)^8 \\
 \mathbf{822656953} &:= (822 + 6 + 5 + 6 + 95 + 3)^3 &= (822 + 65 + 6 - 9 + 53)^3 \\
 \mathbf{843908625} &:= (843 + 9 + 086 + 2 + 5)^3 &= (843 - 9 + 086 + 25)^3 \\
 \mathbf{846590536} &:= (846 + 59 + 05 + 36)^3 &= (8 - 4 + 6 - 5 + 905 + 36)^3 \\
 \mathbf{875213056} &:= (87 + 5 + 21 + 3 + 056)^4 &= (8 - 7 + 52 + 130 - 5 - 6)^4 \\
 \mathbf{895841344} &:= (895 + 8 + 4 + 13 + 44)^3 &= (8 + 958 - 4 - 1 + 3 - 4 + 4)^3 \\
 \mathbf{915498611} &:= (91 + 5 + 4 + 9 + 861 + 1)^3 &= (-9 + 1 - 5 - 4 + 986 + 1 + 1)^3 \\
 \mathbf{916132832} &:= (9 + 16 + 1 + 3 + 28 + 3 + 2)^5 &= (91 + 61 - 3 - 2 - 83 - 2)^5 \\
 \mathbf{921167317} &:= (921 + 1 + 6 + 7 + 31 + 7)^3 &= (921 - 1 + 67 + 3 - 17)^3 \\
 \mathbf{937890625} &:= (9 + 37 + 8 + 90 + 6 + 25)^4 &= (93 + 78 - 9 + 06 + 2 + 5)^4 \\
 \mathbf{946966168} &:= (946 + 9 + 6 + 6 + 1 + 6 + 8)^3 &= (9 + 4 + 6 + 966 - 1 + 6 - 8)^3 \\
 \mathbf{970299000} &:= (970 + 2 + 9 + 9 + 000)^3 &= (970 + 29 - 9 + 000)^3 \\
 \mathbf{973242271} &:= (973 + 2 + 4 + 2 + 2 + 7 + 1)^3 &= (973 + 2 + 42 - 27 + 1)^3 \\
 \mathbf{992436543} &:= (9 + 9 + 24 + 3 + 6 + 5 + 4 + 3)^5 &:= (99 - 24 + 36 - 5 - 43)^5 \\
 \\
 \mathbf{1003875856} &:= (1 + 0038 + 75 + 8 + 56)^4 &= (100 + 38 - 7 + 58 - 5 - 6)^4 \\
 \mathbf{1027243729} &:= (10 + 27 + 243 + 729)^3 &= (1027 + 2 + 43 - 72 + 9)^3 \\
 \mathbf{1051871913} &:= (10 + 5 + 18 + 71 + 913)^3 &= (105 - 1 - 8 + 7 + 1 + 913)^3 \\
 \mathbf{1073283121} &:= (107 + 32 + 8 + 31 + 2 + 1)^4 &= (107 - 3 - 2 + 83 - 1 - 2 - 1)^4 \\
 \mathbf{1073741824} &:= (10 + 7 + 3 + 7 + 4 + 1 + 8 + 24)^5 &= (10 + 7 + 37 + 4 - 18 + 24)^5 \\
 & &= (10 + 7 + 3 - 7 + 4 + 1 + 8 + 2 + 4)^6 \\
 & &= (10 + 7 + 37 - 4 - 18 - 24)^{10} \\
 & &= (10 - 7 - 3 - 7 - 4 - 1 - 8 + 24)^{15}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 &= (10 + 7 + 3 - 7 + 4 - 1 - 8 - 2 - 4)^{30} \\
 \mathbf{1076890625} &:= (10 + 76 + 8 + 906 + 25)^3 &= (1076 + 8 - 90 + 6 + 25)^3 \\
 \mathbf{1108717875} &:= (1 + 10 + 871 + 78 + 75)^3 &= (1108 - 7 + 17 - 8 - 75)^3 \\
 \mathbf{1137893184} &:= (11 + 3 + 7 + 8 + 931 + 84)^3 &= (1 - 1 + 37 - 8 + 931 + 84)^3 \\
 \mathbf{1141166125} &:= (11 + 411 + 6 + 612 + 5)^3 &= (-114 + 1166 - 12 + 5)^3 \\
 \mathbf{1146228736} &:= (11 + 46 + 2 + 2 + 87 + 36)^4 &= (1 + 146 + 2 - 2 + 8 - 7 + 36)^4 \\
 \mathbf{1194389981} &:= (1 + 1 + 9 + 43 + 8 + 998 + 1)^3 &= (1 - 1 + 94 + 3 - 8 - 9 + 981)^3 \\
 \mathbf{1222830961} &:= (12 + 22 + 83 + 09 + 61)^4 &= (122 + 2 + 8 + 3 - 09 + 61)^4 \\
 \mathbf{1275989841} &:= (12 + 7 + 59 + 8 + 98 + 4 + 1)^4 &= (12 + 7 + 5 - 9 + 89 + 84 + 1)^4 \\
 \mathbf{1291467969} &:= (12 + 91 + 4 + 6 + 7 + 969)^3 &= (12 + 91 + 4 + 6 + 7 - 96 + 9)^6 \\
 \mathbf{1389928896} &:= (13 + 8 + 992 + 88 + 9 + 6)^3 &= (138 - 9 + 92 + 889 + 6)^3 \\
 \mathbf{1475789056} &:= (14 + 75 + 7 + 89 + 05 + 6)^4 &= (147 + 5 + 78 - 90 + 56)^4 \\
 \mathbf{1497193984} &:= (14 + 9 + 719 + 398 + 4)^3 &= (1 + 4 - 9 + 71 + 93 + 984)^3 \\
 \mathbf{1536953616} &:= (153 + 6 + 9 + 5 + 3 + 6 + 16)^4 &= (153 + 6 - 9 + 5 + 36 + 1 + 6)^4 \\
 \mathbf{1568239201} &:= (156 + 8 + 23 + 9 + 2 + 01)^4 &= (156 + 8 + 23 - 9 + 20 + 1)^4 \\
 \mathbf{1664966416} &:= (166 + 4 + 9 + 6 + 6 + 4 + 1 + 6)^4 &= (166 + 4 + 9 - 6 - 6 + 41 - 6)^4 \\
 \mathbf{1804229351} &:= (1 + 8 + 042 + 2 + 9 + 3 + 5 + 1)^5 &= (18 - 042 - 2 + 93 + 5 - 1)^5 \\
 \mathbf{1836036801} &:= (183 + 6 + 03 + 6 + 8 + 01)^4 &= (183 - 60 - 3 + 6 + 80 + 1)^4 \\
 \mathbf{1871773696} &:= (18 + 71 + 7 + 7 + 3 + 6 + 96)^4 &= (18 + 7 + 177 - 3 - 6 + 9 + 6)^4 \\
 \mathbf{1934917632} &:= (1 + 9 + 34 + 9 + 1 + 7 + 6 + 3 + 2)^5 &= (1 + 9 + 3 + 49 + 17 - 6 - 3 + 2)^5 \\
 \mathbf{1982119441} &:= (19 + 82 + 11 + 94 + 4 + 1)^4 &= (19 + 82 + 119 - 4 - 4 - 1)^4 \\
 \mathbf{2073071593} &:= (2 + 07 + 30 + 7 + 15 + 9 + 3)^5 &= (20 + 7 + 30 + 7 + 15 - 9 + 3)^5 \\
 \mathbf{2097273616} &:= (20 + 97 + 27 + 3 + 61 + 6)^4 &= (209 + 7 + 27 - 36 + 1 + 6)^4 \\
 \mathbf{2176782336} &:= (2 + 1 + 76 + 78 + 23 + 36)^4 &= (2 + 1 + 7 - 6 + 7 + 8 + 23 - 36)^{12} \\
 \mathbf{2217373921} &:= (22 + 173 + 7 + 3 + 9 + 2 + 1)^4 &= (22 + 173 + 7 + 3 - 9 + 21)^4 \\
 \mathbf{2472973441} &:= (24 + 72 + 9 + 73 + 44 + 1)^4 &= (247 + 2 + 9 + 7 + 3 - 44 - 1)^4 \\
 \mathbf{2562890625} &:= (2 + 56 + 2 + 8 + 90 + 62 + 5)^4 &= (25 - 6 - 2 - 8 + 9 - 06 - 2 + 5)^8 \\
 \mathbf{2608757776} &:= (2 + 60 + 87 + 57 + 7 + 7 + 6)^4 &= (260 + 8 + 7 - 57 + 7 + 7 - 6)^4 \\
 \mathbf{2750058481} &:= (2 + 7 + 50 + 05 + 84 + 81)^4 &= (275 - 005 + 8 - 48 - 1)^4 \\
 \mathbf{2805291225} &:= (28 + 052912 + 25)^2 &= (-2 + 80 + 52912 - 25)^2 \\
 \mathbf{2897022976} &:= (28 + 97 + 022 + 9 + 76)^4 &= (2 + 89 + 70 + 2 + 2 - 9 + 76)^4 \\
 \mathbf{2998219536} &:= (29 + 98 + 2 + 1 + 95 + 3 + 6)^4 &= (29 + 98 + 21 + 95 - 3 - 6)^4 \\
 \mathbf{3208542736} &:= (3 + 208 + 5 + 4 + 2 + 7 + 3 + 6)^4 &= (3 + 208 + 5 + 4 + 27 - 3 - 6)^4 \\
 \mathbf{3268147904} &:= (3 + 2 + 681 + 4 + 790 + 4)^3 &= (-3 + 2 - 6 + 8 + 1479 + 04)^3 \\
 \mathbf{3276800000} &:= (3 + 2 + 7 + 68 + 00000)^5 &= (3 - 2 - 7 + 6 + 80 + 0000)^5 \\
 \mathbf{3486784401} &:= (34 + 86 + 78 + 44 + 01)^4 &= (34 + 8 - 6 - 78 + 4 + 40 + 1)^{20} \\
 \mathbf{3518743761} &:= (3 + 5 + 1 + 8 + 743 + 761)^3 &= (35 - 18 - 7 + 43 - 7 - 6 - 1)^6 \\
 \mathbf{3544535296} &:= (35 + 4 + 4 + 53 + 52 + 96)^4 &= (3 + 544 - 5 + 3 - 5 - 296)^4
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 \mathbf{3707398432} &:= (3 + 7 + 07 + 3 + 9 + 8 + 43 + 2)^5 &= (3 - 70 + 7 + 3 + 98 + 43 - 2)^5 \\
 \mathbf{3722098081} &:= (3 + 72 + 2 + 09 + 80 + 81)^4 &= (3 + 72 + 20 - 9 + 80 + 81)^4 \\
 \mathbf{3899547224} &:= (389 + 954 + 7 + 224)^3 &= (3 + 899 - 54 + 722 + 4)^3 \\
 \mathbf{4097152081} &:= (40 + 97 + 15 + 20 + 81)^4 &= (40 + 9 - 7 - 1 + 5 + 208 - 1)^4 \\
 \mathbf{4256518564} &:= (42 + 5 + 65185 + 6 + 4)^2 &= (-4 + 2 - 5 + 65185 + 64)^2 \\
 \mathbf{4294967296} &:= (42 + 9 + 4 + 96 + 7 + 2 + 96)^4 &= (42 + 9 + 4 + 9 - 67 + 2 + 9 - 6)^{32} \\
 \mathbf{4314825152} &:= (43 + 1482 + 51 + 52)^3 &= (-4 + 3 + 1482 - 5 + 152)^3 \\
 \mathbf{4499860561} &:= (4 + 4 + 99 + 86 + 05 + 61)^4 &= (44 - 9 + 98 + 60 + 5 + 61)^4 \\
 \mathbf{4711998736} &:= (47 + 119 + 9 + 8 + 73 + 6)^4 &= (47 + 119 + 98 + 7 - 3 - 6)^4 \\
 \mathbf{4767078987} &:= (4 + 7 + 670 + 7 + 8 + 987)^3 &= (-4 + 7 - 6 + 707 - 8 + 987)^3 \\
 \mathbf{4921675101} &:= (4 + 921 + 675 + 101)^3 &= (-4 + 9216 - 7510 - 1)^3 \\
 \mathbf{4931550625} &:= (4 + 93 + 155 + 06 + 2 + 5)^4 &= (4 + 931 + 5 - 50 - 625)^4 \\
 \mathbf{5158686976} &:= (51 + 58 + 68 + 6 + 9 + 76)^4 &= (51 + 58 + 6 + 86 - 9 + 76)^4 \\
 \mathbf{5584059449} &:= (5 + 5 + 8 + 40 + 5 + 9 + 4 + 4 + 9)^5 &= (5 + 5 + 8 + 40 + 5 - 9 + 44 - 9)^5 \\
 \mathbf{5887339441} &:= (58 + 87 + 33 + 94 + 4 + 1)^4 &= (-58 - 8 - 7 - 3 + 394 - 41)^4 \\
 \mathbf{6178857875} &:= (61 + 7 + 885 + 7 + 875)^3 &= (-6 + 1788 + 57 + 8 - 7 - 5)^3 \\
 \mathbf{6240321451} &:= (62 + 4 + 03 + 2 + 14 + 5 + 1)^5 &= (62 + 4 + 032 + 1 - 4 - 5 + 1)^5 \\
 \mathbf{6414247921} &:= (64 + 142 + 47 + 9 + 21)^4 &= (-641 + 4 + 2 + 4 - 7 + 921)^4 \\
 \mathbf{6690585616} &:= (66 + 90 + 58 + 56 + 16)^4 &= (6 - 6 + 905 - 8 + 5 - 616)^4 \\
 \mathbf{7269949696} &:= (72 + 6 + 99 + 4 + 96 + 9 + 6)^4 &= (7 + 2 - 6 + 994 - 9 - 696)^4 \\
 \mathbf{7886150416} &:= (7 + 88 + 6 + 150 + 41 + 6)^4 &= (788 + 6 + 1 - 504 + 1 + 6)^4 \\
 \mathbf{8208541201} &:= (8 + 2 + 085 + 4 + 1 + 201)^4 &= (-8 + 20 + 85 + 4 - 1 + 201)^4 \\
 \mathbf{8303765625} &:= (8 + 3 + 03 + 7 + 6 + 5 + 6 + 2 + 5)^6 &= (83 - 03 + 7 - 6 - 5 - 6 - 25)^6 \\
 \mathbf{9039207968} &:= (9 + 039 + 20 + 7 + 9 + 6 + 8)^5 &= (90 - 3 + 92 - 079 + 6 - 8)^5 \\
 \mathbf{9509900499} &:= (9 + 50 + 9 + 9 + 004 + 9 + 9)^5 &= (950 - 9 - 900 + 49 + 9)^5 \\
 \mathbf{9597924961} &:= (95 + 9 + 7 + 92 + 49 + 61)^4 &= (9 + 5 - 9 + 7 - 9 + 249 + 61)^4 \\
 \mathbf{9718142104} &:= (9 + 7 + 1 + 8 + 1 + 4 + 2104)^3 &= (-9 + 7 + 18 + 14 + 2104)^3 \\
 \mathbf{9911994481} &:= (99 + 11 + 99448 + 1)^2 &= (99119 - 9 + 448 + 1)^2 \\
 \\
 \mathbf{10355301121} &:= (1 + 03 + 5 + 5 + 301 + 1 + 2 + 1)^4 &= (1 + 035 - 5 + 301 - 12 - 1)^4 \\
 & &= (-1 + 0355 - 30 - 1 - 1 - 2 - 1)^4 \\
 & &= (10 + 35 - 5 + 301 - 1 - 21)^4 \\
 & &= (-103 + 5 - 5 + 301 + 121)^4 \\
 \mathbf{10460353203} &:= (1 + 04 + 6 + 03 + 5 + 3 + 2 + 03)^7 &= (1 + 04 - 6 + 03 + 5 + 3 + 20 - 3)^7 \\
 & &= (10 + 4 - 60 - 3 + 53 + 20 + 3)^7 \\
 & &= (10 - 4 + 6 + 035 + 3 - 20 - 3)^7 \\
 & &= (1 + 04 - 6 + 03 + 5 - 3 + 2 - 03)^{21} \\
 & &= (10 + 4 - 60 + 35 - 3 + 20 - 3)^{21}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 \mathbf{10750371856} &:= (107 + 50 + 3 + 71 + 85 + 6)^4 &= (10 - 46 + 03 + 53 - 20 + 3)^{21} \\
 & &= (10 + 7503 - 7185 - 6)^4 \\
 & &= (1 - 07 + 5 + 0371 + 8 - 56)^4 \\
 & &= (10 + 7 + 503 - 7 - 185 - 6)^4 \\
 & &= (-107 + 503 - 71 + 8 - 5 - 6)^4 \\
 \mathbf{11019960576} &:= (1 + 1 + 0199 + 60 + 57 + 6)^4 &= (1 + 10 + 19 - 9 + 60 - 57 - 6)^8 \\
 & &= (1 + 101 + 99 + 60 + 57 + 6)^4 \\
 & &= (1 + 101 - 9 - 9 - 60 - 5 - 7 + 6)^8 \\
 & &= (11 + 01 - 9 + 96 - 05 - 76)^8 \\
 & &= (110 + 1 + 9 + 9 - 60 - 57 + 6)^8 \\
 \mathbf{11105365924} &:= (1 + 1 + 105365 + 9 + 2 + 4)^2 &= (1 + 1 + 105365 - 9 + 24)^2 \\
 \mathbf{11405819251} &:= (1 + 1405 + 819 + 25 + 1)^3 &= (1 + 1405 - 81 + 925 + 1)^3 \\
 \mathbf{11574317056} &:= (1 + 1 + 57 + 43 + 170 + 56)^4 \\
 &:= (1 + 157 + 43 + 1 + 70 + 56)^4 &= (1 + 1 + 5 + 7 - 4 + 317 - 05 + 6)^4 \\
 & &= (1 + 157 + 4 - 3 + 170 + 5 - 6)^4 \\
 & &= (11 + 5 + 7 + 431 - 70 - 56)^4 \\
 \mathbf{12230590464} &:= (1 + 2230 + 59 + 04 + 6 + 4)^3 &= (-12 + 2305 + 9 + 04 - 6 + 4)^3 \\
 & &= (12 - 2 + 30 + 5 + 9 + 04 - 6 - 4)^6 \\
 & &= (122 - 3 + 05 - 90 + 4 + 6 + 4)^6 \\
 & &= (1 - 22 - 305 - 90 + 464)^6 \\
 \mathbf{12246522625} &:= (1 + 2 + 24 + 6 + 5 + 2262 + 5)^3 \\
 &:= (1 + 22 + 4 + 6 + 5 + 2262 + 5)^3 \\
 &:= (1 + 2246 + 5 + 2 + 26 + 25)^3 \\
 &:= (1 + 2246 + 5 + 22 + 6 + 25)^3 &= (1 + 2246 + 5 - 2 - 2 + 62 - 5)^3 \\
 & &= (1 - 2 - 2 + 46 + 5 + 2262 - 5)^3 \\
 \mathbf{12296370321} &:= (1 + 2 + 296 + 3 + 7 + 03 + 21)^4 \\
 &:= (1 + 229 + 6 + 3 + 70 + 3 + 21)^4 \\
 &:= (1 + 229 + 63 + 7 + 032 + 1)^4 &= (1 + 2 + 296 - 3 + 70 - 32 - 1)^4 \\
 & &= (1 + 22 - 9 - 6 - 3 + 7 + 0321)^4 \\
 & &= (-12 + 296 + 370 - 321)^4 \\
 & &= (12 - 2 + 9 + 63 - 70 + 321)^4 \\
 \mathbf{12444741136} &:= (1 + 244 + 4 + 7 + 41 + 1 + 36)^4 \\
 &:= (1 + 244 + 4 + 74 + 1 + 1 + 3 + 6)^4 \\
 &:= (1 + 244 + 47 + 4 + 1 + 1 + 36)^4 &= (1 + 2 - 4 - 4 + 474 + 1 - 136)^4 \\
 & &= (12 + 444 - 7 + 4 - 113 - 6)^4 \\
 & &= (1 - 24 - 44 - 7 + 411 + 3 - 6)^4 \\
 \mathbf{12503322161} &:= (125 + 03 + 32 + 2161)^3 \\
 &:= (125 + 033 + 2 + 2161)^3 &= (1 + 2503 + 32 - 216 + 1)^3
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 \mathbf{12535672267} &:= (1 + 2 + 5 + 35 + 6 + 7 + 2267)^3 &= (1 - 2 + 53 + 5 + 6 - 7 + 2267)^3 \\
 & &= (125 + 3 - 5 - 67 + 2267)^3 \\
 \mathbf{12681938368} &:= (12 + 6 + 8 + 1938 + 368)^3 &= (-1 + 2681 + 9 + 3 + 8 - 368)^3 \\
 \mathbf{12897917761} &:= (1 + 2 + 8 + 9 + 79 + 177 + 61)^4 \\
 &:= (1 + 2 + 8 + 97 + 91 + 77 + 61)^4 \\
 &:= (1 + 289 + 7 + 9 + 17 + 7 + 6 + 1)^4 \\
 &:= (12 + 89 + 7 + 91 + 77 + 61)^4 \\
 &:= (128 + 9 + 7 + 9 + 177 + 6 + 1)^4 \\
 &:= (128 + 97 + 91 + 7 + 7 + 6 + 1)^4 &= (1 + 28 - 9 + 79 + 177 + 61)^4 \\
 & &= (12 + 89 + 7 - 9 + 177 + 61)^4 \\
 & &= (128 - 9 + 79 + 1 + 77 + 61)^4 \\
 & &= (1354 + 935 - 9 + 104)^3 \\
 \mathbf{13549359104} &:= (1354 + 935 + 91 + 04)^3 \\
 \mathbf{13680577296} &:= (1 + 36 + 80 + 57 + 72 + 96)^4 \\
 &:= (13 + 6 + 8 + 05 + 7 + 7 + 296)^4 &= (1 + 368 - 057 + 7 + 29 - 6)^4 \\
 & &= (1 - 3 + 6 - 8 + 057 - 7 + 296)^4 \\
 & &= (136 + 80 + 57 + 72 - 9 + 6)^4 \\
 & &= (-13 - 6 + 80 + 577 - 296)^4 \\
 \mathbf{13841287201} &:= (1 + 3 + 8 + 41 + 2 + 87 + 201)^4 \\
 &:= (1 + 3 + 8 + 41 + 287 + 2 + 01)^4 \\
 &:= (1 + 38 + 4 + 12 + 87 + 201)^4 \\
 &:= (138 + 4 + 128 + 72 + 01)^4 &= (1 + 38 + 412 - 87 - 20 - 1)^4 \\
 & &= (13 + 8 + 412 - 87 - 2 - 01)^4 \\
 & &= (138 + 4 + 1 - 2 + 8 - 7 + 201)^4 \\
 & &= (1 + 3 + 8 + 4 + 1 + 28 + 7 - 2 - 01)^6 \\
 & &= (138 - 4 + 1 - 287 + 201)^6 \\
 & &= (13 - 84 + 128 - 7 - 2 + 01)^6 \\
 & &= (1 + 3 - 84 + 1 + 2 + 87 - 2 - 01)^{12} \\
 & &= (13 - 84 - 12 + 87 + 2 + 01)^{12} \\
 & &= (138 - 41 - 2 - 87 - 2 + 01)^{12} \\
 & &= (1 - 40 + 14 - 95 + 2531)^3 \\
 \mathbf{14014952531} &:= (1401 + 4 + 952 + 53 + 1)^3 \\
 \mathbf{14025517307} &:= (1 + 4 + 02 + 5 + 51 + 7 + 30 + 7)^5 \\
 &:= (1 + 4 + 02 + 55 + 1 + 7 + 30 + 7)^5 \\
 &:= (1 + 40 + 2 + 5 + 5 + 17 + 30 + 7)^5 \\
 &:= (14 + 02 + 5 + 5 + 1 + 73 + 07)^5 \\
 &:= (14 + 025 + 51 + 7 + 3 + 07)^5 &= (1 + 40 - 2 + 55 + 17 + 3 - 07)^5 \\
 & &= (140 + 2 - 55 - 17 + 30 + 7)^5 \\
 & &= (14 - 02 + 55 + 17 + 30 - 7)^5 \\
 & &= (1404 - 9 + 8 + 5 + 8 + 997)^3 \\
 \mathbf{14049858997} &:= (1404 + 98 + 5 + 899 + 7)^3 &= (1404 - 9 + 8 + 5 + 8 + 997)^3
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 \mathbf{14331199589} &:= (14 + 331 + 1995 + 89)^3 &= (1 + 433 + 1 + 1995 + 8 - 9)^3 \\
 & &= (1433 + 1 + 1 + 995 + 8 - 9)^3 \\
 \mathbf{14331920656} &:= (1 + 4 + 3 + 319 + 2 + 06 + 5 + 6)^4 \\
 &:= (1 + 43 + 31 + 9 + 206 + 56)^4 &= (1 + 433 - 1 - 92 + 06 + 5 - 6)^4 \\
 & &= (1 - 4 + 331 - 9 + 20 + 6 - 5 + 6)^4 \\
 & &= (1 - 43 + 319 - 2 + 065 + 6)^4 \\
 & &= (14 - 3 - 319 - 2 + 0656)^4 \\
 \mathbf{14688124849} &:= (1468 + 8 + 124 + 849)^3 &= (1 + 46 + 8 - 81 + 2484 - 9)^3 \\
 \mathbf{14693280768} &:= (1 + 4 + 6 + 9 + 3 + 2 + 8 + 07 + 68)^5 \\
 &:= (1 + 4 + 69 + 3 + 2 + 8 + 07 + 6 + 8)^5 &= (1 + 4 - 693 + 28 + 0768)^5 \\
 &:= (1 + 46 + 9 + 3 + 28 + 07 + 6 + 8)^5 &= (146 - 93 + 2 - 8 - 07 + 68)^5 \\
 & &= (14 - 6 - 9 - 32 + 80 - 7 + 68)^5 \\
 \mathbf{14835483601} &:= (14 + 8 + 354 + 8 - 36 + 01)^4 \\
 &:= (148 + 3 + 54 + 83 + 60 + 1)^4 &= (1 + 4 + 8 + 354 - 8 - 3 - 6 - 01)^4 \\
 & &= (1 + 4 - 83 + 5 + 483 - 60 - 1)^4 \\
 \mathbf{15142552424} &:= (1 + 5 + 14 + 25 + 5 + 2424)^3 \\
 &:= (15 + 1 + 4 + 25 + 5 + 2424)^3 &= (1 + 51 - 4 + 2 + 5 - 5 + 2424)^3 \\
 \mathbf{15179306176} &:= (1517 + 930 + 6 + 17 + 6)^3 &= (-1 - 517 + 9 + 3061 - 76)^3 \\
 \mathbf{15308412587} &:= (1530 + 841 + 25 + 87)^3 &= (-15 + 3084 - 1 + 2 - 587)^3 \\
 & &= (-153 + 08 + 41 + 2587)^3 \\
 \mathbf{15352201216} &:= (153 + 52 + 20 + 121 + 6)^4 &= (1 + 535 + 2 - 201 + 21 - 6)^4 \\
 & &= (153 - 5 + 220 - 1 - 21 + 6)^4 \\
 & &= (15 + 352 + 201 - 216)^4 \\
 \mathbf{15386239549} &:= (1 + 5 + 3 + 8 + 6 + 23 + 9 + 5 + 49)^5 \\
 &:= (1 + 5 + 3 + 8 + 62 + 3 + 9 + 5 + 4 + 9)^5 \\
 &:= (1 + 5 + 38 + 6 + 2 + 39 + 5 + 4 + 9)^5 \\
 &:= (1 + 5 + 3 + 86 + 2 + 3 - 9 + 5 + 4 + 9)^5 \\
 &:= (15 + 3 + 8 + 6 + 2 + 3 + 9 + 54 + 9)^5 \\
 &:= (15 + 38 + 6 + 23 + 9 + 5 + 4 + 9)^5 &= (1 + 5 + 386 - 239 + 5 - 49)^5 \\
 & &= (1 + 53 + 86 - 2 - 39 + 5 - 4 + 9)^5 \\
 & &= (15 + 38 + 62 + 39 - 54 + 9)^5 \\
 & &= (153 - 8 - 6 + 23 - 9 + 5 - 49)^5 \\
 \mathbf{15882300625} &:= (1 + 5 + 8 + 8 + 2 + 300 + 6 + 25)^4 \\
 &:= (1 + 5 + 88 + 230 + 06 + 25)^4 &= (1 + 5 - 8 - 8 - 2 + 300 + 62 + 5)^4 \\
 & &= (1 - 5 + 88 + 2 + 300 - 6 - 25)^4 \\
 & &= (-158 - 82 - 30 + 0625)^4 \\
 \mathbf{16426010896} &:= (1 + 64 + 260 + 10 + 8 + 9 + 6)^4 &= (1 + 6 + 4 + 260 - 1 - 08 + 96)^4
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{16983563041} &:= (16 + 9 + 8 + 3 + 5 - 63 + 041)^8 \\ &:= (169 + 83 + 5 + 63 + 041)^4 \end{aligned}$$

$$\mathbf{17253512704} := (17 + 2535 + 1 + 27 + 04)^3$$

$$\mathbf{17596287801} := (1759 + 6 + 28 + 7 + 801)^3$$

$$\mathbf{18129265883} := (1 + 812 + 926 + 5 + 883)^3$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{18141126721} &:= (1 + 81 + 4 + 11 + 267 + 2 + 1)^4 \\ &:= (181 + 4 + 112 + 67 + 2 + 1)^4 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{18337088853} &:= (1833 + 708 + 8 + 85 + 3)^3 \\ &:= (1833 + 708 + 88 + 5 + 3)^3 \end{aligned}$$

$$\mathbf{18525482136} := (1 + 85 + 2548 + 2 + 1 + 3 + 6)^3$$

$$\mathbf{18525482136} := (1 + 85 + 2548 + 21 - 3 - 6)^3$$

$$\mathbf{18525482136} := (1852 + 5 + 4 + 821 - 36)^3$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{18539817921} &:= (1 + 85 + 3 + 98 + 179 + 2 + 1)^4 \\ &:= (18 + 53 + 98 + 179 + 21)^4 \\ &:= (185 + 3 + 98 + 1 + 79 + 2 + 1)^4 \end{aligned}$$

$$\mathbf{19486825371} := (1948 + 682 + 53 + 7 + 1)^3$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{19987173376} &:= (1 + 9 - 9 + 8 + 7 + 17 + 337 + 6)^4 \\ &:= (1 + 99 + 87 + 173 + 3 + 7 + 6)^4 \\ &:= (19 + 98 + 7 + 173 + 3 + 76)^4 \\ &:= (199 + 87 + 1 + 7 + 3 + 3 + 76)^4 \\ &:= (199 + 87 + 1 + 73 + 3 + 7 + 6)^4 \end{aligned}$$

$$\mathbf{20301732352} := (2 + 0301 + 73 + 2352)^3$$

$$\begin{aligned} &= (1 + 64 - 2 - 601 + 0896)^4 \\ &= (16 + 426 - 01 - 089 + 6)^4 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} &= (1 + 69 - 8 - 3 + 5 - 6 + 304 - 1)^4 \\ &= (16 + 983 - 5 - 630 - 4 + 1)^4 \\ &= (16 - 9 - 8 + 356 + 3 + 04 - 1)^4 \\ &= (1 + 6 + 98 + 3 - 56 - 30 - 4 + 1)^8 \\ &= (16 + 98 - 35 - 63 + 04 - 1)^8 \\ &= (169 - 83 - 56 + 30 - 41)^8 \end{aligned}$$

$$= (1 - 72 - 53 + 5 - 1 + 2704)^3$$

$$= (1 + 759 + 62 + 8 - 780 + 1)^6$$

$$= (17 - 59 + 6 + 2 + 8 + 78 - 01)^6$$

$$= (175 - 96 - 28 - 7 + 8 - 01)^6$$

$$= (-18 - 1 + 2 - 9 + 2658 - 8 + 3)^3$$

$$= (18 + 1 + 411 + 2 + 6 - 72 + 1)^4$$

$$= (1 + 8 + 1 + 411 - 26 - 7 - 21)^4$$

$$= (1 - 81 + 411 + 2 + 6 + 7 + 21)^4$$

$$= (1833 - 70 - 8 + 885 - 3)^3$$

$$= (1 + 8 + 539 - 81 - 7 - 92 + 1)^4$$

$$= (18 + 539 - 8 - 179 - 2 + 1)^4$$

$$= (185 + 3 + 98 - 1 - 7 + 92 - 1)^4$$

$$= (185 + 3 - 9 + 8 + 179 + 2 + 1)^4$$

$$= (1 + 94 - 8 + 68 + 2537 - 1)^3$$

$$= (1 - 99 + 87 + 1 + 7 + 3 + 376)^4$$

$$= (19 - 9 - 8 + 71 - 73 + 376)^4$$

$$= (19 - 9 - 8 + 717 - 337 - 6)^4$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 &:= (203 + 0173 + 2352)^3 &= (2030 - 1 + 732 - 35 + 2)^3 \\
 \mathbf{20415837456} &:= (204 + 1 + 5 + 83 + 74 + 5 + 6)^4 &= (-204 + 1 + 583 - 7 + 4 - 5 + 6)^4 \\
 &:= (2 + 0415 - 83 - 7 + 45 + 6)^4 &= (20 - 4 + 1 - 58 - 37 + 456)^4 \\
 \\
 \mathbf{20632736881} &:= (2 + 06 + 3 + 273 + 6 + 8 + 81)^4 \\
 &:= (2 + 06 + 3 + 273 + 6 + 88 + 1)^4 \\
 &:= (20 + 6 + 3 + 273 + 68 + 8 + 1)^4 \\
 &:= (20 + 6 + 327 + 3 + 6 + 8 + 8 + 1)^4 \\
 &:= (20 + 63 + 273 + 6 + 8 + 8 + 1)^4 \\
 &:= (206 + 3 + 2 + 73 + 6 + 8 + 81)^4 \\
 &:= (206 + 3 + 2 + 73 + 6 + 88 + 1)^4 &= (2 + 06 + 3 + 2 + 7 + 368 - 8 - 1)^4 \\
 & &= (20 - 6 - 327 + 3 + 688 + 1)^4 \\
 & &= (20 - 63 - 27 + 368 + 81)^4 \\
 \\
 \mathbf{20706256936} &:= (2070 + 625 + 6 + 9 + 36)^3 &= (207 + 06 + 2569 - 36)^3 \\
 \\
 \mathbf{21003416576} &:= (2 + 1 + 003 + 41 + 6 + 57 + 6)^5 \\
 &:= (2 + 1 + 0034 + 1 + 65 + 7 + 6)^5 \\
 &:= (2 + 1 + 0034 + 16 + 57 + 6)^5 \\
 &:= (2 + 10 + 03 + 4 + 16 + 5 + 76)^5 \\
 &:= (2 + 10 + 034 + 1 + 6 + 57 + 6)^5 \\
 &:= (21 + 003 + 4 + 1 + 6 + 5 + 76)^5 &= (2 + 100 - 3 + 41 - 6 - 5 - 7 - 6)^5 \\
 & &= (21 - 003 + 41 + 6 + 57 - 6)^5 \\
 & &= (2 - 1 - 003 + 41 + 6 - 5 + 76)^5 \\
 & &= (210 - 03 - 4 - 16 + 5 - 76)^5 \\
 \\
 \mathbf{21293813776} &:= (2 + 129 + 38 + 137 + 76)^4 \\
 &:= (212 + 9 + 3 + 8 + 137 + 7 + 6)^4 &= (21 + 29 - 38 - 1 + 377 - 6)^4 \\
 & &= (212 + 93 - 8 - 1 + 3 + 7 + 76)^4 \\
 & &= (21 - 29 + 381 + 3 + 7 - 7 + 6)^4 \\
 & &= (2 - 1 - 2 - 9 - 381 - 3 + 776)^4 \\
 & &= (215 + 3135 - 576 + 8)^3 \\
 \\
 \mathbf{21531355768} &:= (2153 + 1 + 3 + 557 + 68)^3 \\
 \\
 \mathbf{21924480357} &:= (2 + 1 + 9 + 2 + 4 + 4 + 80 + 3 + 5 + 7)^5 \\
 &:= (2 + 19 + 2 + 4 + 48 + 035 + 7)^5 \\
 &:= (2 + 19 + 2 + 44 + 8 + 035 + 7)^5 \\
 &:= (2 + 19 + 24 + 4 + 8 + 03 + 57)^5 \\
 &:= (21 + 9 + 24 + 48 + 03 + 5 + 7)^5 &= (2 - 1 + 92 + 44 + 8 - 035 + 7)^5 \\
 & &= (219 + 24 - 4 - 80 - 35 - 7)^5 \\
 & &= (21 - 9 - 244 - 8 + 0357)^5 \\
 \\
 \mathbf{21970650625} &:= (219 + 70 + 65 + 06 + 25)^4 &= (-21 - 97 - 06 + 506 - 2 + 5)^4 \\
 \\
 \mathbf{22164361129} &:= (2 + 2164 + 3 + 611 + 29)^3 &= (22 + 1 - 64 + 3 + 61 + 1 + 29)^6
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 &= (2 - 21 + 6 - 43 + 6 + 112 - 9)^6 \\
 &= (221 + 64 - 361 + 129)^6 \\
 &= (2216 - 4 - 3 + 611 - 2 - 9)^3 \\
 \\
 \mathbf{22354272513} &:= (2 + 23 + 54 + 2725 + 13)^3 \\
 &:= (22 + 3 + 54 + 2725 + 13)^3 \\
 &:= (223 + 54 + 27 + 2513)^3 \\
 &:= (2 + 2 + 3542 - 725 - 1 - 3)^3 \\
 \\
 \mathbf{22430753361} &:= (2 + 2 + 4 + 3 + 07 + 5 + 3 + 361)^4 \\
 &:= (2 + 2 + 4 + 30 + 7 + 5 + 336 + 1)^4 \\
 &:= (2 + 2 + 4 + 307 + 5 + 3 + 3 + 61)^4 \\
 &:= (2 + 2 + 430 - 75 - 33 + 61)^4 \\
 &:= (22 - 4 + 3 + 07 - 5 + 3 + 361)^4 \\
 &:= (2 - 24 - 3 + 075 + 336 + 1)^4 \\
 \\
 \mathbf{22663495936} &:= (2 + 2 + 6 + 6 + 349 + 5 + 9 + 3 + 6)^4 \\
 &:= (2 + 266 + 3 + 4 + 9 + 5 + 93 + 6)^4 \\
 &:= (2 + 266 + 3 + 4 + 95 + 9 + 3 + 6)^4 \\
 &:= (2 + 266 + 3 + 49 + 59 + 3 + 6)^4 \\
 &:= (226 + 6 + 3 + 49 + 5 + 93 + 6)^4 \\
 &:= (226 + 63 + 49 + 5 + 9 + 36)^4 \\
 &:= (22 + 6 + 6 + 349 + 5 + 9 - 3 - 6)^4 \\
 &:= (2 + 2 + 6 - 63 - 495 + 936)^4 \\
 &:= (226 + 6 + 34 + 95 - 9 + 36)^4 \\
 \\
 \mathbf{22785532875} &:= (2 + 2785 + 5 + 3 + 28 + 7 + 5)^3 \\
 &:= (2278 + 5 + 532 + 8 + 7 + 5)^3 \\
 &:= (2278 + 553 - 2 + 8 - 7 + 5)^3 \\
 &:= (2 - 27 - 8 - 5 - 5 + 3 + 2875)^3 \\
 \\
 \mathbf{22809653056} &:= (2 + 2809 + 6 + 5 + 3 + 05 + 6)^3 \\
 &:= (2280 + 9 + 6 + 530 + 5 + 6)^3 \\
 &:= (2 + 2809 - 6 + 5 - 30 + 56)^3 \\
 &:= (-228 + 09 - 6 + 5 + 3056)^3 \\
 \\
 \mathbf{22877577568} &:= (2 + 2 + 8 + 7 + 7 + 5 + 7 + 7 + 5 + 68)^5 \\
 &:= (2 + 287 - 75 - 77 - 5 - 6 - 8)^5 \\
 &:= (22 + 87 + 757 - 756 + 8)^5 \\
 &:= (2 - 28 + 77 + 57 + 7 + 5 + 6 - 8)^5 \\
 &:= (22 - 8 - 7 - 7 + 57 + 75 - 6 - 8)^5 \\
 \\
 \mathbf{23372600161} &:= (2 + 3 + 372 + 6 + 001 + 6 + 1)^4 \\
 &:= (2 + 337 - 2 - 6 - 001 + 61)^4 \\
 &:= (233 - 7 - 2 + 6 + 00161)^4 \\
 \\
 \mathbf{23887872000} &:= (2 + 3 + 88 + 787 + 2000)^3 \\
 &:= (-2 + 3 + 8 + 878 - 7 + 2000)^3 \\
 \\
 \mathbf{24098215696} &:= (2 + 4 + 098 + 215 + 69 + 6)^4 \\
 &:= (2 + 40 + 98 + 2 + 156 + 96)^4 \\
 &:= (2 + 409 + 8 - 21 + 5 + 6 - 9 - 6)^4 \\
 &:= (-24 + 0982 - 1 - 569 + 6)^4 \\
 &:= (240 - 9 + 8 + 2 + 1 + 56 + 96)^4 \\
 &:= (-2 - 409 + 821 + 5 - 6 - 9 - 6)^4
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 \mathbf{24363778699} &:= (2436 + 377 + 8 + 69 + 9)^3 \\
 \mathbf{24363778699} &:= (2436 + 377 + 86 + 9 - 9)^3 &= (-24 + 3637 - 7 - 8 - 699)^3 \\
 \mathbf{24591257856} &:= (24 + 5 + 91 + 257 + 8 + 5 + 6)^4 \\
 &:= (245 + 9 + 1 + 2 + 5 + 78 + 56)^4 &= (2 - 4 + 591 - 257 + 8 + 56)^4 \\
 & &= (245 - 9 + 1 + 25 + 78 + 56)^4 \\
 & &= (2 - 459 + 1 - 2 + 5 - 7 + 856)^4 \\
 \mathbf{24794911296} &:= (2 + 4 + 7 + 9 + 4 + 9 + 1 + 1 + 2 + 9 + 6)^6 = (24 + 79 + 49 + 1 - 1 - 2 - 96)^6 \\
 & &= (247 + 94 + 9 - 1 + 1 - 296)^6 \\
 & &= (24 - 79 - 4 - 9 - 1 + 129 - 6)^6 \\
 \mathbf{24840596881} &:= (248 + 4 + 05 - 9 + 68 + 81)^4 \\
 &:= (248 + 40 + 5 + 9 + 6 + 8 + 81)^4 &= (2 + 484 - 05 - 9 - 68 - 8 + 1)^4 \\
 & &= (248 + 40 + 5 + 9 + 6 + 88 + 1)^4 \\
 & &= (2 - 4 - 8 + 405 - 9 - 6 + 8 + 8 + 1)^4 \\
 \mathbf{26376683281} &:= (2 + 6 + 37 + 6 + 68 + 3 + 281)^4 \\
 &:= (2 + 6 + 37 + 66 + 8 + 3 + 281)^4 \\
 &:= (26 + 3 + 76 + 6 + 8 + 3 + 281)^4 \\
 &:= (263 + 7 + 6 + 6 + 8 + 32 + 81)^4 &= (2 + 6 + 376 + 68 + 32 - 81)^4 \\
 & &= (263 + 76 + 68 + 3 + 2 - 8 - 1)^4 \\
 & &= (26 - 3 - 7 + 66 - 8 + 328 + 1)^4 \\
 & &= (263 - 76 - 68 + 3 + 281)^4 \\
 \mathbf{27189441343} &:= (2 + 718 + 944 + 1343)^3 &= (2718 - 9 - 44 - 1 + 343)^3 \\
 \mathbf{27512614111} &:= (2 + 7 + 5 + 1 + 2 + 6 + 1 + 4 + 1 + 1 + 1)^7 = (27 + 5 - 126 + 14 + 111)^7 \\
 & &= (275 + 1 - 261 + 4 + 11 + 1)^7 \\
 & &= (27 - 51 + 26 - 1 + 41 - 11)^7 \\
 \mathbf{27625773167} &:= (276 + 2577 + 3 + 167)^3 &= (2 - 76 + 2 + 5 - 77 + 3167)^3 \\
 & &= (-2762 + 5773 - 1 + 6 + 7)^3 \\
 \mathbf{27982932961} &:= (2 + 7 + 9 + 8 + 293 + 29 + 61)^4 \\
 &:= (2 + 7 + 9 + 82 + 9 + 3 + 296 + 1)^4 \\
 &:= (27 + 9 + 8 + 29 + 329 + 6 + 1)^4 \\
 &:= (27 + 9 + 8 + 293 + 2 + 9 + 61)^4 \\
 &:= (279 + 8 + 29 + 3 + 29 + 61)^4 \\
 &:= (279 + 82 + 9 + 3 + 29 + 6 + 1)^4 &= (27 - 9 + 82 + 9 + 3 + 296 + 1)^4 \\
 & &= (279 + 8 + 2 - 9 + 32 + 96 + 1)^4 \\
 & &= (27 - 9 + 8 + 2 - 9 + 329 + 61)^4 \\
 \mathbf{28122197921} &:= (2 + 812 + 2197 + 9 + 21)^3 \\
 &:= (28 + 1 + 2219 + 792 + 1)^3 \\
 &:= (2812 + 2 + 197 + 9 + 21)^3 &= (2 - 81 + 2 + 2197 + 921)^3 \\
 \mathbf{28813025536} &:= (2 + 8 + 8 + 1 + 302 + 55 + 36)^4
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 &:= (2 + 8 + 8 + 130 + 255 + 3 + 6)^4 \\
 &:= (2 + 8 + 81 + 30 + 255 + 36)^4 \\
 &:= (2 + 8 + 81 + 302 + 5 + 5 + 3 + 6)^4 \\
 &:= (2 + 88 + 1 + 30 + 255 + 36)^4 \\
 &:= (2 + 88 + 1 + 302 + 5 + 5 + 3 + 6)^4 \\
 &:= (288 + 1 + 30 + 2 + 55 + 36)^4 &= (288 + 130 + 25 + 5 - 36)^4 \\
 & &= (28 - 8 - 1 + 302 + 55 + 36)^4 \\
 & &= (2 - 88 - 13 - 025 + 536)^4 \\
 \mathbf{28934443000} &:= (2 + 8 + 9 + 3 + 44 + 4 + 3000)^3 &= (28 - 9 + 3 + 44 + 4 + 3000)^3 \\
 \mathbf{29132817533} &:= (2 - 9 + 1328 + 1753 + 3)^3 &= (291 - 3 + 2817 + 5 - 33)^3 \\
 &:= (2913 + 2 + 81 + 75 + 3 + 3)^3 &= (29 - 16 + 12 + 3055 - 2)^3 \\
 \mathbf{29161230552} &:= (2 + 9 + 1 + 6 + 1 + 2 + 3055 + 2)^3 \\
 \mathbf{29376588816} &:= (293 + 7 + 6 + 5 + 8 + 8 + 81 + 6)^4 &= (29 + 376 - 58 - 8 + 81 - 6)^4 \\
 &:= (293 + 7 + 6 + 5 + 8 + 88 + 1 + 6)^4 &= (-2 - 93 - 76 + 588 - 8 - 1 + 6)^4 \\
 &:= (293 + 76 + 5 + 8 + 8 + 8 + 16)^4 \\
 \mathbf{29661450625} &:= (296 + 6 + 1 + 45 + 062 + 5)^4 &= (29 + 6 - 61 + 450 - 6 + 2 - 5)^4 \\
 &:= (296 + 61 + 45 + 06 + 2 + 5)^4 &= (296 + 61 - 4 + 5 + 062 - 5)^4 \\
 & &= (-2 - 966 + 1450 - 62 - 5)^4 \\
 \mathbf{29675828736} &:= (2967 + 58 + 28 + 7 + 36)^3 &= (296 - 75 + 8 + 2873 - 6)^3 \\
 \mathbf{29704593673} &:= (2970 + 4 + 5 + 9 + 36 + 73)^3 &= (2970 - 45 + 93 + 6 + 73)^3 \\
 &:= (2970 + 45 + 9 + 3 + 67 + 3)^3 &= (2990 - 6 - 4 + 68 - 8 + 64)^3 \\
 \mathbf{29906468864} &:= (2990 + 6 + 4 + 6 + 8 + 86 + 4)^3 &= (-29 - 9 + 6 + 4 + 3150 - 16)^3 \\
 \mathbf{29964315016} &:= (2996 + 43 + 1 + 50 + 16)^3 \\
 \mathbf{30167363897} &:= (3016 + 7 + 3 + 63 + 8 + 9 + 7)^3 &= (3016 + 7 + 3 - 6 - 3 + 89 + 7)^3 \\
 &:= (3016 + 7 + 36 + 38 + 9 + 7)^3 &= (3042 + 9 + 77 - 18 + 4 + 8)^3 \\
 \mathbf{30429771848} &:= (3042 + 9 + 7 + 7 + 1 + 8 + 48)^3 \\
 \mathbf{30517578125} &:= (3 + 05 + 1 + 7 + 5 + 78 + 1 + 25)^5 &= (3051 + 7 + 57 + 8 - 1 - 2 + 5)^3 \\
 &:= (3 + 05 + 1 + 75 + 7 + 8 + 1 + 25)^5 &= (30 + 5 + 175 - 78 - 12 + 5)^5 \\
 &:= (3 + 05 + 17 + 5 + 78 + 12 + 5)^5 &= (3 - 05 - 1 - 7 - 5 + 7 + 8 + 125)^5 \\
 &:= (30 + 5 + 1 + 7 + 57 + 8 + 12 + 5)^5 &= (305 - 17 - 57 - 81 - 25)^5 \\
 &:= (30 + 51 + 7 + 5 + 7 + 8 + 12 + 5)^5 &= (3 + 05 + 1 + 7 + 5 - 7 + 8 - 12 - 5)^{15} \\
 & &= (30 + 5 + 17 + 5 - 78 + 1 + 25)^{15}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 &= (3 - 051 - 7 - 57 - 8 + 125)^{15} \\
 \mathbf{30528476176} &:= (30 + 5 + 284 + 76 + 17 + 6)^4 \\
 &:= (30 + 52 + 84 + 76 + 176)^4 \\
 &:= (305 + 2 + 8 + 4 + 76 + 17 + 6)^4 \\
 &:= (305 + 2 + 84 + 7 + 6 + 1 + 7 + 6)^4 \\
 &:= (305 + 28 + 4 + 7 + 61 + 7 + 6)^4 \\
 &= (30 + 528 + 4 - 7 - 61 - 76)^4 \\
 &= (-3 - 052 + 8 + 476 - 17 + 6)^4 \\
 &= (305 - 2 - 8 - 47 - 6 + 176)^4 \\
 \mathbf{30693697091} &:= (3069 + 36 + 9 + 7 + 09 + 1)^3 \\
 &= (3069 + 3 + 6 - 9 + 70 - 9 + 1)^3 \\
 \mathbf{30723115968} &:= (3072 + 31 + 1 + 5 + 9 + 6 + 8)^3 \\
 &= (30 - 72 + 3115 - 9 + 68)^3 \\
 &= (3072 - 31 + 159 - 68)^3 \\
 \mathbf{30988732221} &:= (30 + 9 + 8 + 873 + 2221)^3 \\
 &:= (3098 + 8 + 7 + 3 + 2 + 2 + 21)^3 \\
 &:= (3098 + 8 + 7 + 3 + 2 + 22 + 1)^3 \\
 &:= (3098 + 8 + 7 + 3 + 22 + 2 + 1)^3 \\
 &= (3 - 098 + 8 + 7 + 3222 - 1)^3 \\
 \mathbf{31018339288} &:= (3101 + 8 + 3 + 3 + 9 + 2 + 8 + 8)^3 \\
 &= (3101 + 83 + 3 - 9 - 28 - 8)^3 \\
 \mathbf{31414372081} &:= (31 + 4 + 1 + 4 + 372 + 08 + 1)^4 \\
 &:= (314 + 14 + 3 + 7 + 2 + 081)^4 \\
 &= (3 + 1 + 41 + 437 + 20 - 81)^4 \\
 &= (314 + 1 + 43 + 72 - 08 - 1)^4 \\
 &= (31 - 414 + 3 + 720 + 81)^4 \\
 \mathbf{31524548679} &:= (3 + 15 + 2454 + 8 + 679)^3 \\
 &= (3152 + 45 - 48 - 6 + 7 + 9)^3 \\
 &= (3152 - 4 - 54 - 8 - 6 + 79)^3 \\
 \mathbf{31757969376} &:= (3 + 1 + 7 + 5 + 7 + 9 + 6 + 9 + 3 + 76)^5 \\
 &:= (3 + 1 + 7 + 5 + 79 + 6 + 9 + 3 + 7 + 6)^5 \\
 &:= (3 + 1 + 75 + 7 + 9 + 6 + 9 + 3 + 7 + 6)^5 \\
 &:= (3 + 17 + 5 + 7 + 9 + 69 + 3 + 7 + 6)^5 \\
 &= (3 + 1 + 7 + 5 + 7 + 96 - 9 + 3 + 7 + 6)^5 \\
 &= (31 + 7 + 5 + 7 - 9 + 69 + 3 + 7 + 6)^5 \\
 &= (3 - 17 + 5 - 796 + 937 - 6)^5 \\
 \mathbf{32015587041} &:= (320 + 1 + 5 + 5 + 87 + 04 + 1)^4 \\
 &:= (320 + 15 + 5 + 8 + 70 + 4 + 1)^4 \\
 &= (-3 - 20 - 1 + 558 - 70 - 41)^4 \\
 \mathbf{32309356625} &:= (3 + 2 + 3093 + 56 + 6 + 25)^3 \\
 &= (3230 + 9 + 3 - 56 + 6 - 2 - 5)^3 \\
 \mathbf{32319410176} &:= (3 + 231 + 9 + 4 + 1 + 0176)^4 \\
 &:= (3 + 231 + 9 + 4 + 101 + 76)^4 \\
 &:= (323 + 1 + 9 + 4 + 10 + 1 + 76)^4 \\
 &:= (323 + 19 + 4 + 1 + 01 + 76)^4 \\
 &= (-3 + 231 + 94 + 101 + 7 - 6)^4 \\
 &= (32 + 3 - 19 + 410 - 1 - 7 + 6)^4 \\
 &= (323 - 1 + 94 + 10 - 1 - 7 + 6)^4 \\
 \mathbf{32645273536} &:= (3 + 2645 + 2 + 7 + 3 + 536)^3 \\
 &= (3264 + 5 + 2 - 73 - 5 - 3 + 6)^3
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{33038369407} &:= (3 + 3 + 03 + 8 + 3 + 6 + 94 + 07)^5 \\ &:= (3 + 3 + 038 + 3 + 69 + 4 + 07)^5 \\ &:= (3 + 30 + 3 + 8 + 3 + 69 + 4 + 07)^5 \\ &:= (3 + 30 + 38 + 36 + 9 + 4 + 07)^5 \\ &:= (33 + 03 + 8 + 3 + 69 + 4 + 07)^5 \\ &:= (33 + 038 + 36 + 9 + 4 + 07)^5 \end{aligned}$$

$$\mathbf{33138024128} := (3 + 3138 + 02 + 41 + 28)^3$$

$$\mathbf{33168984597} := (3 + 3168 + 9 + 8 + 4 + 5 + 9 + 7)^3$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{33243864241} &:= (3 + 3 + 2 + 4 + 386 + 4 + 24 + 1)^4 \\ &:= (3 + 3 + 24 + 386 + 4 + 2 + 4 + 1)^4 \\ &:= (3 + 324 + 3 + 8 + 6 + 42 + 41)^4 \\ &:= (3 + 324 + 3 + 8 + 64 + 24 + 1)^4 \\ &:= (3 + 324 + 3 + 86 + 4 + 2 + 4 + 1)^4 \\ &:= (332 + 4 + 38 + 6 + 4 + 2 + 41)^4 \\ &:= (332 + 4 + 38 + 6 + 42 + 4 + 1)^4 \end{aligned}$$

$$\mathbf{33417362861} := (3 + 341 + 7 + 3 + 6 + 2861)^3$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{34828517376} &:= (3 + 4 + 8 + 28 + 5 + 1 + 7 + 376)^4 \\ &:= (3 + 48 + 285 + 17 + 3 + 76)^4 \\ &:= (348 + 2 + 8 + 51 + 7 + 3 + 7 + 6)^4 \\ &:= (348 + 28 + 5 + 1 + 7 + 37 + 6)^4 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{35152125121} &:= (3 + 5 + 152 + 1 + 251 + 21)^4 \\ &:= (35 + 152 + 125 + 121)^4 \\ &:= (351 + 5 + 2 + 1 + 2 + 51 + 21)^4 \\ &:= (351 + 5 + 21 + 2 + 51 + 2 + 1)^4 \\ &:= (351 + 52 + 1 + 2 + 5 + 1 + 21)^4 \\ &:= (351 + 52 + 1 + 25 + 1 + 2 + 1)^4 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} &= (3264 + 52 - 73 - 53 + 6)^3 \\ &= (-326 - 4 - 5 + 2 - 7 + 3536)^3 \\ &= (3264 - 5 + 2 - 73 + 5 - 3 + 6)^3 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} &= (3 + 30 - 3 - 836 + 940 - 7)^5 \\ &= (-330 + 38 - 3 + 6 + 9 + 407)^5 \\ &= (33 - 03 - 8 + 3 + 69 + 40 - 7)^5 \\ &= (3313 - 80 + 2 + 4 + 1 - 28)^3 \\ &= (3 + 3168 + 98 - 4 - 59 + 7)^3 \\ &= (3316 - 8 - 98 - 4 + 5 + 9 - 7)^3 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} &= (33 + 243 - 86 - 4 + 241)^4 \\ &= (332 - 4 + 38 + 64 + 2 - 4 - 1)^4 \\ &= (3 - 3 - 2 - 4 + 386 + 42 + 4 + 1)^4 \\ &= (33 - 243 - 8 + 642 + 4 - 1)^4 \\ &= (334 + 17 + 3 + 6 + 2861)^3 \\ &= (3341 - 73 - 62 + 8 + 6 + 1)^3 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} &= (3 + 482 + 8 - 5 + 17 + 3 - 76)^4 \\ &= (348 + 2 + 8 - 5 - 1 + 7 - 3 + 76)^4 \\ &= (34 - 8 - 28 + 51 + 7 + 376)^4 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 & := (351 + 52 + 12 + 5 + 12 + 1)^4 & = (35 + 1 + 521 + 2 - 5 - 121)^4 \\
 \mathbf{36136489216} & := (3 + 61 + 3 + 64 + 89 + 216)^4 \\
 & := (36 + 1 + 364 + 8 + 9 + 2 + 16)^4 \\
 & := (361 + 3 + 6 + 48 + 9 + 2 + 1 + 6)^4 \\
 & := (361 + 36 + 4 + 8 + 9 + 2 + 16)^4 & = (3 + 61 + 364 + 8 + 9 - 2 - 1 - 6)^4 \\
 & & = (361 - 36 + 4 + 89 + 2 + 16)^4 \\
 & & = (3 - 61 - 3 - 6 + 489 - 2 + 16)^4 \\
 & & = (36 - 1 - 3 - 6 - 489 + 21 + 6)^4 \\
 \\
 \mathbf{37141383841} & := (3 + 7 + 1 + 4 + 1 + 38 + 384 + 1)^4 \\
 & := (37 + 1 + 4 + 1 + 3 + 8 + 384 + 1)^4 \\
 & := (37 + 1 + 4 + 1 + 383 + 8 + 4 + 1)^4 \\
 & := (371 + 4 + 1 + 3 + 8 + 3 + 8 + 41)^4 \\
 & := (371 + 4 + 13 + 8 + 38 + 4 + 1)^4 \\
 & := (371 + 41 + 3 + 8 + 3 + 8 + 4 + 1)^4 & = (3 - 71 + 413 + 8 + 3 + 84 - 1)^4 \\
 & & = (371 - 4 - 1 + 38 + 38 - 4 + 1)^4 \\
 & & = (3 - 7 - 14 - 1 - 383 + 841)^4 \\
 \\
 \mathbf{37822859361} & := (3 + 7 + 8 + 22 + 8 + 5 - 93 + 61)^8 \\
 & := (3 + 78 + 2 + 285 + 9 + 3 + 61)^4 \\
 & := (378 + 2 + 2 + 8 + 5 + 9 + 36 + 1)^4 & = (3 + 78 - 228 + 593 - 6 + 1)^4 \\
 & & = (37 + 8 - 2 + 28 + 5 + 9 - 3 - 61)^8 \\
 & & = (378 + 2 + 2 + 85 + 9 - 36 + 1)^4 \\
 & & = (378 + 2 - 2 + 8 + 5 - 9 - 361)^8 \\
 & & = (3 - 782 + 285 + 936 - 1)^4 \\
 \\
 \mathbf{38167092496} & := (3 + 8 + 167 + 09 + 249 + 6)^4 \\
 & := (381 + 6 + 7 + 09 + 24 + 9 + 6)^4 & = (38 + 1 + 6 - 7 - 092 + 496)^4 \\
 & & = (381 + 67 - 09 + 2 + 4 - 9 + 6)^4 \\
 & & = (3 - 8 - 1 - 6 + 709 - 249 - 6)^4 \\
 \\
 \mathbf{39213900625} & := (39 + 2 + 1 + 390 + 06 + 2 + 5)^4 \\
 & := (392 + 1 + 39 + 006 + 2 + 5)^4 \\
 & := (392 + 13 + 9 + 006 + 25)^4 & = (392 - 13 + 9 + 0062 - 5)^4 \\
 & & = (-39 - 2 - 139 + 00625)^4 \\
 \\
 \mathbf{40282095616} & := (4 + 0282 + 095 + 61 + 6)^4 \\
 & := (402 + 8 + 2 + 09 + 5 + 6 + 16)^4 & = (402 + 8 - 2 + 095 - 61 + 6)^4 \\
 & & = (40 - 2 + 8 - 209 - 5 + 616)^4 \\
 \\
 \mathbf{41371966801} & := (413 + 7 + 1 + 9 + 6 + 6 + 8 + 01)^4 \\
 & & = (4 - 137 + 1 - 96 + 680 - 1)^4 \\
 & & = (413 - 71 + 96 + 6 + 8 - 01)^4 \\
 \\
 \mathbf{42483805456} & := (4 + 2 + 4 + 8 + 380 + 5 + 45 + 6)^4 \\
 & := (4 + 2 + 48 + 380 + 5 + 4 + 5 + 6)^4
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 & := (42 + 4 + 8 + 380 + 5 + 4 + 5 + 6)^4 & = (4 - 2 + 4 - 83 + 80 - 5 + 456)^4 \\
 & & = (424 + 8 - 3 + 80 - 54 + 5 - 6)^4 \\
 \mathbf{43204003424} & := (4 + 32 + 040 + 034 + 24)^5 \\
 & := (43 + 2 + 040 + 03 + 42 + 4)^5 \\
 & := (43 + 20 + 40 + 03 + 4 + 24)^5 & = (432 + 040 - 0342 + 4)^5 \\
 \mathbf{43617904801} & := (4 + 361 + 79 + 04 + 8 + 01)^4 \\
 & := (43 + 6 + 17 - 90 + 480 + 1)^4 & = (4 + 361 + 7 + 90 + 4 - 8 - 01)^4 \\
 & & = (436 + 17 + 9 + 04 - 8 - 01)^4 \\
 \mathbf{44386483761} & := (4 + 4 + 386 + 48 + 3 + 7 + 6 + 1)^4 \\
 & := (44 + 386 + 4 + 8 + 3 + 7 + 6 + 1)^4 & = (4 + 4 + 386 - 4 + 83 - 7 - 6 - 1)^4 \\
 & & = (4 + 438 + 6 - 4 + 83 - 7 - 61)^4 \\
 & & = (443 - 86 - 4 + 8 + 37 + 61)^4 \\
 \mathbf{44840334375} & := (4 + 4 + 8 + 4 + 03 + 34 + 3 + 75)^5 \\
 & := (4 + 4 + 8 + 4 + 033 + 4 + 3 + 75)^5 \\
 & := (4 + 4 + 8 + 40 + 3 + 34 + 37 + 5)^5 \\
 & := (4 + 4 + 8 + 40 + 33 + 4 + 37 + 5)^5 \\
 & := (4 + 48 + 4 + 03 + 34 + 37 + 5)^5 \\
 & := (4 + 48 + 4 + 033 + 4 + 37 + 5)^5 & = (4 + 4 - 8 + 403 - 343 + 75)^5 \\
 & & = (44 + 8 + 4 + 03 + 34 + 37 + 5)^5 \\
 & & = (44 + 8 + 4 + 033 + 4 + 37 + 5)^5 \\
 & & = (44 + 8 + 40 - 33 + 4 - 3 + 75)^5 \\
 \mathbf{46525874176} & := (4 + 6 + 5 + 2 + 5 + 87 + 4 + 17 + 6)^5 \\
 & := (4 + 6 + 5 + 2 + 58 + 7 + 41 + 7 + 6)^5 \\
 & := (4 + 6 + 5 + 25 + 8 + 7 + 4 + 1 + 76)^5 \\
 & := (4 + 6 + 5 + 25 + 8 + 74 + 1 + 7 + 6)^5 \\
 & := (4 + 6 + 52 + 5 + 8 + 7 + 41 + 7 + 6)^5 \\
 & := (4 + 65 + 25 + 8 + 7 + 4 + 17 + 6)^5 \\
 & := (46 + 5 + 2 + 58 + 7 + 4 + 1 + 7 + 6)^5 \\
 & := (46 + 52 + 5 + 8 + 7 + 4 + 1 + 7 + 6)^5 & = (4 + 65 - 2 + 58 + 7 + 4 + 1 - 7 + 6)^5 \\
 & & = (46 + 5 + 258 + 7 - 4 - 176)^5 \\
 & & = (46 - 5 + 2 - 58 + 74 + 1 + 76)^5 \\
 & & = (4 - 65 + 258 - 7 - 41 - 7 - 6)^5 \\
 \mathbf{47156728336} & := (4 + 7 + 156 + 7 + 283 + 3 + 6)^4 \\
 & := (4 + 71 + 5 + 67 + 283 + 36)^4 \\
 & := (47 + 1 + 5 + 67 + 2 + 8 + 336)^4 & = (4 - 71 + 567 - 28 + 3 - 3 - 6)^4 \\
 & & = (471 - 5 - 67 + 28 + 3 + 36)^4 \\
 \mathbf{47359345032} & := (4 + 7 + 3593 + 4 + 5 + 03 + 2)^3
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 & := (4 + 73 + 59 + 3450 + 32)^3 & = (47 + 3593 - 4 - 50 + 32)^3 \\
 \mathbf{47971512576} & := (4 + 79 + 71 + 51 + 257 + 6)^4 & = (47 - 9 + 7 - 151 - 2 + 576)^4 \\
 & & = (4 - 7 - 97 - 1 + 5 - 12 + 576)^4 \\
 & & = (479 - 7 - 15 - 1 + 25 - 7 - 6)^4 \\
 \\
 \mathbf{48382841521} & := (4 + 8 + 3 + 8 + 2 + 8 + 415 + 21)^4 & \\
 & := (4 + 8 + 3 + 8 + 28 + 415 + 2 + 1)^4 & \\
 & := (4 + 8 + 382 + 8 + 41 + 5 + 21)^4 & \\
 & := (48 + 382 + 8 + 4 + 1 + 5 + 21)^4 & = (4 + 8 - 3 + 8 - 28 - 41 + 521)^4 \\
 & & = (48 + 3 - 8 + 2 + 8 + 415 + 2 - 1)^4 \\
 & & = (48 + 382 - 8 + 41 + 5 + 2 - 1)^4 \\
 & & = (483 + 82 - 84 - 15 + 2 + 1)^4 \\
 \\
 \mathbf{49108313528} & := (4 + 91 + 08 + 31 + 3528)^3 & \\
 & := (49 + 1 + 083 + 1 + 3528)^3 & = (4 - 9 + 108 + 31 + 3528)^3 \\
 & & = (491 + 08 + 3135 + 28)^3 \\
 \\
 \mathbf{51312965696} & := (5 + 1 + 3129 + 6 + 569 + 6)^3 & = (51 + 3 + 1 + 2965 + 696)^3 \\
 \mathbf{51395862232} & := (-5 + 1 + 3958 - 6 + 2 - 232)^3 & = (5 + 1395 + 86 + 2232)^3 \\
 \mathbf{52204938256} & := (5 + 2 + 20 + 4 + 9 + 382 + 56)^4 & \\
 & := (5 + 22 + 04 + 9 + 382 + 56)^4 & = (522 + 04 + 9 - 38 - 25 + 6)^4 \\
 & := (52 + 20 + 4 + 9 + 382 + 5 + 6)^4 & = (-5 - 2 - 2 + 049 + 382 + 56)^4 \\
 & & = (-52 - 2 + 0493 + 8 + 25 + 6)^4 \\
 \\
 \mathbf{52523350144} & := (5 + 2 + 5 + 2 + 3 + 3 + 5 + 01 + 4 + 4)^7 & = (5 + 2 + 523 - 3 - 501 + 4 + 4)^7 \\
 & & = (525 + 2 - 3 + 3 - 501 + 4 + 4)^7 \\
 & & = (52 - 5 - 23 - 35 + 01 + 44)^7 \\
 & & = (5 + 25 - 2 + 3718 + 6 - 2 - 5)^3 \\
 \\
 \mathbf{52523718625} & := (5 + 2 + 5 + 2 + 3718 + 6 + 2 + 5)^3 & \\
 \mathbf{53527912321} & := (5 + 3 + 52 + 7 + 91 + 2 + 321)^4 & \\
 & := (5 + 35 + 27 + 91 + 2 + 321)^4 & \\
 & := (5 + 352 + 7 + 91 + 2 + 3 + 21)^4 & \\
 & := (5 + 352 + 7 + 91 + 23 + 2 + 1)^4 & \\
 & := (5 + 352 + 79 + 1 + 23 + 21)^4 & \\
 & := (5 + 352 + 79 + 12 + 32 + 1)^4 & \\
 & := (53 + 5 + 2 + 7 + 91 + 2 + 321)^4 & \\
 & := (53 + 5 + 279 + 123 + 21)^4 & = (5 + 3 + 527 - 9 - 1 - 23 - 21)^4 \\
 & & = (53 + 527 - 91 - 2 - 3 - 2 - 1)^4 \\
 & & = (535 + 279 - 12 - 321)^4 \\
 \\
 \mathbf{54875873536} & := (5 + 48 + 7 + 58 + 7 + 353 + 6)^4 & = (5 + 4 + 8 + 7 + 5 - 8 - 73 + 536)^4 \\
 & & = (54 + 87 + 5 + 8 - 73 - 53 - 6)^8 \\
 & & = (54 + 87 - 5 + 8 - 7 + 353 - 6)^4
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\mathbf{55132330616} := (551 + 3233 + 06 + 16)^3$$

$$\mathbf{56249134561} := (5 + 6 + 2 + 4 + 9 + 1 + 3 + 456 + 1)^4$$

$$:= (5 + 62 + 4 + 9 + 1 + 345 + 61)^4$$

$$\mathbf{59072816401} := (59 + 07 + 2 + 8 + 16 + 401)^4$$

$$\mathbf{59797108943} := (5 + 9 + 7 + 9 + 7 + 1 + 08 + 94 + 3)^5$$

$$:= (5 + 9 + 7 + 9 + 7 + 10 + 89 + 4 + 3)^5$$

$$:= (5 + 9 + 7 + 97 + 1 + 08 + 9 + 4 + 3)^5$$

$$:= (5 + 97 + 9 + 7 + 1 + 08 + 9 + 4 + 3)^5$$

$$:= (5 + 97 + 97 - 108 + 9 + 43)^5$$

$$:= (59 + 7 + 9 + 7 + 1 + 08 + 9 + 43)^5$$

$$\mathbf{60037250625} := (6 + 00372 + 50 + 62 + 5)^4$$

$$:= (60 + 0372 + 50 + 6 + 2 + 5)^4$$

$$\mathbf{61917364224} := (6 + 1 + 9 + 1 + 73 + 6 + 42 + 2 + 4)^5$$

$$:= (6 + 1 + 91 + 7 + 3 + 6 + 4 + 2 + 24)^5$$

$$:= (6 + 1 + 91 + 7 + 3 + 6 + 4 + 22 + 4)^5$$

$$:= (6 + 19 + 17 + 36 + 42 + 24)^5$$

$$:= (61 + 9 + 1 + 7 + 36 + 4 + 2 + 24)^5$$

$$:= (61 + 9 + 1 + 7 + 36 + 4 + 22 + 4)^5$$

$$:= (61 + 9 + 17 + 3 + 6 + 42 + 2 + 4)^5$$

$$\mathbf{62523502209} := (6 + 2 + 5 + 2 + 35 + 02 + 2 + 09)^6$$

$$:= (6 + 252 + 3502 + 209)^3$$

$$\mathbf{64097340625} := (6 + 4 + 09 + 73 + 40 + 6 + 2 + 5)^5$$

$$:= (6 + 4 + 097 + 3 + 4 + 06 + 25)^5$$

$$:= (6 + 40 + 9 + 73 + 4 + 06 + 2 + 5)^5$$

$$= (5 - 4 + 8 - 758 + 735 + 36)^8$$

$$= (548 + 7 + 5 - 87 + 3 + 5 - 3 + 6)^4$$

$$= (548 + 75 + 8 - 73 - 536)^8$$

$$= (5 + 513 - 2 + 3306 - 16)^3$$

$$= (56 + 2 - 4 - 9 - 13 + 456 - 1)^4$$

$$= (562 + 49 - 134 + 5 + 6 - 1)^4$$

$$= (-56 - 2 - 49 - 1 + 34 + 561)^4$$

$$= (5 + 90 + 7 - 2 + 8 - 16 + 401)^4$$

$$= (590 - 7 + 2 - 81 - 6 - 4 - 01)^4$$

$$= (59 - 7 + 9 - 7 - 10 + 8 + 94 - 3)^5$$

$$= (59 - 797 - 10 + 894 - 3)^5$$

$$= (6 + 003 + 7 - 2 + 506 - 25)^4$$

$$= (600 + 3 - 72 - 5 - 06 - 25)^4$$

$$= (-60 - 03 - 72 + 5 + 0625)^4$$

$$= (61 + 9 + 17 - 3 - 6 + 42 + 24)^5$$

$$= (619 + 173 - 642 - 2 - 4)^5$$

$$= (61 - 9 - 1 + 73 - 6 + 4 - 2 + 24)^5$$

$$= (6 - 1 - 91 - 7 + 3 + 6 + 4 + 224)^5$$

$$= (6 - 25 + 23 + 50 - 2 + 20 - 9)^6$$

$$= (62 - 5 + 235 - 0220 - 9)^6$$

$$= (-625 - 23 + 502 + 209)^6$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 & := (64 + 09 + 7 + 34 + 06 + 25)^5 & = (640 + 9 - 73 - 406 - 25)^5 \\
 & & = (64 - 09 + 73 - 40 + 62 - 5)^5 \\
 & & = (6 - 409 - 73 - 4 + 0625)^5 \\
 \mathbf{64192192064} & := (6 + 4 + 1921 + 9 + 2064)^3 & = (6 + 4192 - 192 - 06 + 4)^3 \\
 \mathbf{64524128256} & := (6 + 45 + 2 + 412 + 8 + 25 + 6)^4 \\
 & := (6 + 452 + 4 + 1 + 2 + 8 + 25 + 6)^4 \\
 & := (6 + 452 + 4 + 1 + 28 + 2 + 5 + 6)^4 \\
 & := (64 + 5 + 2 + 412 + 8 + 2 + 5 + 6)^4 \\
 & := (64 + 52 + 4 + 128 + 256)^4 & = (6 + 4 + 524 + 1 - 28 - 2 + 5 - 6)^4 \\
 & & = (64 + 524 - 1 - 2 - 82 - 5 + 6)^4 \\
 & & = (645 + 2 + 4 - 128 - 25 + 6)^4 \\
 \mathbf{65037750625} & := (6 + 5 + 0377 + 50 + 62 + 5)^4 \\
 & := (6 + 50 + 377 + 5 + 062 + 5)^4 \\
 & := (65 + 0377 + 50 + 6 + 2 + 5)^4 & = (6 + 503 - 7 + 7 + 5 - 06 + 2 - 5)^4 \\
 & & = (-6 - 50 + 3 + 77 + 506 - 25)^4 \\
 \mathbf{65939264000} & := (6 + 5 + 9 + 3 + 9 + 2 + 6 + 4000)^3 \\
 & := (65 + 9 + 3926 + 40 + 00)^3 & = (6 + 5 + 9 + 3 - 9 + 26 + 4000)^3 \\
 & & = (65 - 9 - 3 - 9 + 2 - 6 + 4000)^3 \\
 \mathbf{66597028096} & := (66 + 59 + 7 + 0280 + 96)^4 & = (6 + 65 - 9 + 70 + 280 + 96)^4 \\
 & & = (665 - 970 - 2 + 809 + 6)^4 \\
 \mathbf{68184176641} & := (6 + 8 + 1 + 8 + 417 + 6 + 64 + 1)^4 \\
 & := (6 + 8 + 1 + 8 + 417 + 66 + 4 + 1)^4 \\
 & := (68 + 1 + 8 + 417 + 6 + 6 + 4 + 1)^4 & = (6 + 81 - 8 + 417 + 6 + 6 + 4 - 1)^4 \\
 & & = (68 - 18 - 4 - 176 + 641)^4 \\
 & & = (681 - 84 - 17 - 6 - 64 + 1)^4 \\
 \mathbf{68719476736} & := (6 + 8 + 7 + 1 + 9 + 4 + 7 + 6 + 7 + 3 + 6)^6 = (-687 + 19 + 4767 + 3 - 6)^3 \\
 & & = (6 + 87 + 1 + 9 + 476 - 73 + 6)^4 \\
 & & = (68 + 7 - 1 - 9 + 476 + 7 - 36)^4 \\
 & & = (687 - 1 - 94 - 7 + 6 - 73 - 6)^4 \\
 \mathbf{68719476736} & := (6 + 8 + 7 + 1 + 9 + 4 + 7 + 6 + 7 + 3 + 6)^6 = (6 + 87 + 19 - 4 - 7 + 6 - 7 - 36)^6 \\
 & & = (68 + 7 + 1 - 9 - 4 - 7 + 6 - 7 + 3 + 6)^6 \\
 & & = (68 + 71 + 9 - 47 + 6 - 7 - 36)^6 \\
 \mathbf{68719476736} & := (6 + 8 + 7 + 1 + 9 + 4 + 7 + 6 + 7 + 3 + 6)^6 = (6 + 87 + 1 - 9 - 47 - 6 - 7 - 3 - 6)^9 \\
 & & = (68 + 7 + 19 - 47 - 67 + 36)^9 \\
 & & = (687 + 19 - 4 - 7 - 673 - 6)^9 \\
 \mathbf{68719476736} & := (6 + 8 + 7 + 1 + 9 + 4 + 7 + 6 + 7 + 3 + 6)^6 = (6 + 8 - 7 - 19 + 4 - 7 - 6 - 7 + 36)^{12} \\
 & & = (6 + 87 - 1 - 9 - 4 - 7 - 67 - 3 + 6)^{12} \\
 & & = (68 - 71 - 94 + 76 - 7 + 36)^{12}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 68719476736 &:= (6+8+7+1+9+4+7+6+7+3+6)^6 = (6+87-194+76-7+36)^{18} \\ &= (68+7+1+9-4-7-67+3-6)^{18} \\ &= (687-19-4+76-736)^{18} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 68719476736 &:= (6+8+7+1+9+4+7+6+7+3+6)^6 = (6+87+1+9+4-76+7-36)^{36} \\ &= (687+1+9+47-6-736)^{36} \\ &= (68-71-9-47-6+73-6)^{36} \end{aligned}$$

$$69072400727 := (6+9+072+4007+2+7)^3 = (6-9+072+4007+27)^3$$

$$\begin{aligned} 69257922561 &:= (6+9+257+9+225+6+1)^4 = (6+92+579-225+61)^4 \\ &= (692-5+79+2-256+1)^4 \\ &= (6-9-25-7+9-22+561)^4 \\ &= (692-57-92-25-6+1)^4 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 69799526416 &:= (6+9+7+9+9+52+6+416)^4 \\ &:= (69+79+95+264+1+6)^4 = (6+979-9-52+6-416)^4 \\ &= (69-79+9+526-4-1-6)^4 \\ &= (697-9+95-264+1-6)^4 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 71443409521 &:= (7+1+4+43+409+52+1)^4 \\ &:= (7+1+44+3+409+52+1)^4 \\ &:= (7+1+443+4+09+52+1)^4 \\ &:= (7+14+434+09+52+1)^4 \\ &:= (71+4+4+3+409+5+21)^4 \\ &:= (71+4+4+340+95+2+1)^4 \\ &:= (71+44+340+9+52+1)^4 = (71+443-4-09-5+21)^4 \\ &= (7-1-4+43-40-9+521)^4 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 72407429632 &:= (72+4074+2+9+6+3+2)^3 = (72+4074+29-6-3+2)^3 \\ &= (7-2+4074-2+96-3-2)^3 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 74247530256 &:= (7+4+2+475+3+025+6)^4 \\ &:= (7+4+247+5+3+0256)^4 \\ &:= (7+424+7+53+025+6)^4 \\ &:= (7+424+75+3+02+5+6)^4 = (7+424+75-3+025-6)^4 \\ &= (74+2+475-30+2+5-6)^4 \\ &= (742+4+7-5+30-256)^4 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 74818113841 &:= (7+48+1+81+1+384+1)^4 \\ &:= (7+481+8+1+13+8+4+1)^4 \\ &:= (7+481+8+11+3+8+4+1)^4 = (7+481+81-13+8-41)^4 \\ &= (748-181-1-38-4-1)^4 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 77199941512 &:= (7+71+9+9+9+4151+2)^3 \\ &:= (77+1+9+9+9+4151+2)^3 = (7+7+1+99-9+4151+2)^3 \end{aligned}$$

$$79502005521 := (7+9+502+005+5+2+1)^4 = (7-9+502+005+5+21)^4$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 \mathbf{80102584576} &:= (8 + 01 + 02 + 58 + 457 + 6)^4 &= (8 + 01 + 02 + 584 - 57 - 6)^4 \\
 & &= (80 - 10 + 2 + 5 - 8 + 457 + 6)^4 \\
 \mathbf{81136812032} &:= (8 + 1 + 1 + 3 + 6 + 8 + 120 + 3 + 2)^5 \\
 &:= (8 + 1 + 1 + 3 + 6 + 81 + 20 + 32)^5 \\
 &:= (8 + 1 + 1 + 36 + 81 + 20 + 3 + 2)^5 \\
 &:= (8 + 113 + 6 + 8 + 12 + 03 + 2)^5 \\
 &:= (8 + 113 + 6 - 8 - 1 + 2 + 032)^5 \\
 &:= (81 + 1 + 3 + 6 + 8 + 1 + 20 + 32)^5 \\
 &:= (81 + 1 + 36 + 8 + 1 + 20 + 3 + 2)^5 \\
 &:= (81 + 13 + 6 + 8 + 12 + 032)^5 &= (811 + 3 - 681 + 20 - 3 + 2)^5 \\
 & &= (81 - 13 + 68 + 1 + 20 - 3 - 2)^5 \\
 \mathbf{81924750625} &:= (8 + 19 + 2 + 475 + 06 + 25)^4 &= (8 + 1 + 92 - 47 + 506 - 25)^4 \\
 & &= (819 + 247 - 506 - 25)^4 \\
 & &= (81 - 92 - 4 - 75 + 0625)^4 \\
 \mathbf{83625443117} &:= (8 + 36 + 2 + 5 + 4 + 4311 + 7)^3 &= (8 - 3 - 6 + 2 + 54 + 4311 + 7)^3 \\
 & &= (8 - 3 - 62 + 5 + 4431 + 1 - 7)^3 \\
 \mathbf{83777829136} &:= (83 + 77 + 78 + 291 + 3 + 6)^4 &= (-8 + 377 - 7 + 82 + 91 - 3 + 6)^4 \\
 & &= (8377 - 7829 - 1 - 3 - 6)^4 \\
 \mathbf{83841135993} &:= (8 + 3 + 8 + 4 + 11 + 35 - 9 + 93)^5 \\
 &:= (8 + 3 + 84 + 1 + 1 + 35 + 9 + 9 + 3)^5 \\
 &:= (83 + 8 + 4 + 1 + 1 + 35 + 9 + 9 + 3)^5 &= (83 + 8 + 41 - 13 - 59 + 93)^5 \\
 & &= (-838 + 4 + 1 + 1 - 3 - 5 + 993)^5 \\
 \mathbf{86617093024} &:= (8 + 6 + 6 + 1 + 70 + 9 + 30 + 24)^5 \\
 &:= (8 + 6 + 6 + 17 + 093 + 024)^5 \\
 &:= (8 + 66 + 17 + 09 + 30 + 24)^5 \\
 &:= (86 + 6 + 17 + 09 + 30 + 2 + 4)^5 &= (8 + 6 + 6 + 170 - 9 - 3 - 024)^5 \\
 & &= (86 + 61 + 70 - 9 - 30 - 24)^5 \\
 & &= (86 - 6 - 17 + 093 + 02 - 4)^5 \\
 \mathbf{87824421125} &:= (878 + 2442 + 1125)^3 &= (8 - 7 + 8 - 2 + 4421 + 12 + 5)^3 \\
 \mathbf{87943022623} &:= (8 + 794 + 3022 + 623)^3 \\
 &:= (87 + 9 + 4302 + 26 + 23)^3 &= (87 - 9 + 4302 + 2 + 62 + 3)^3 \\
 \mathbf{89434562048} &:= (8 + 9 + 4345 + 62 + 048)^3 \\
 &:= (89 + 4345 + 6 + 20 + 4 + 8)^3 &= (-8 + 9 - 43 + 4562 - 048)^3 \\
 \mathbf{89526025681} &:= (8 + 9 + 5 + 260 + 256 + 8 + 1)^4 \\
 & &= (8 + 9 + 526 + 02 + 5 + 6 - 8 - 1)^4 \\
 & &= (-8 + 952 - 60 - 256 - 81)^4 \\
 & &= (89 - 52 + 602 - 5 - 6 - 81)^4 \\
 \mathbf{92982304900} &:= (9 + 2 + 9 + 8 + 2 + 304900)^2 &= (-9 + 29 + 8 + 2 + 304900)^2 \\
 \mathbf{93519144481} &:= (9 + 3 + 5 + 1 + 9 + 1 + 44 + 481)^4
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 &:= (9 + 3 + 5 + 1 + 9 + 1 + 444 + 81)^4 \\
 &:= (9 + 3 + 519 + 1 + 4 + 4 + 4 + 8 + 1)^4 \\
 &:= (9 + 35 + 1 + 9 + 14 + 4 + 481)^4 \\
 &:= (9 + 35 + 19 + 1 + 4 + 4 + 481)^4 &= (9 + 3 + 51 - 9 + 14 + 4 + 481)^4 \\
 & &= (93 + 5 + 1 + 91 + 444 - 81)^4 \\
 & &= (-9 - 3 - 51 - 9 + 144 + 481)^4 \\
 \\
 \mathbf{94445023464} &:= (9 + 4 + 4450 + 23 + 4 + 64)^3 \\
 &:= (9 + 4445 + 02 + 34 + 64)^3 &= (9 + 44 + 4502 - 3 + 4 - 6 + 4)^3 \\
 & &= (-9 - 4 + 4 + 4 + 5023 - 464)^3 \\
 \\
 \mathbf{95565066496} &:= (9 + 5 + 5 + 6 + 506 + 6 + 4 + 9 + 6)^4 \\
 & &= (9 + 5 + 565 - 06 - 6 + 4 - 9 - 6)^4 \\
 & &= (9 + 556 + 50 - 66 + 4 + 9 - 6)^4 \\
 & &= (9 - 55 - 65 + 0664 + 9 - 6)^4 \\
 \\
 \mathbf{96947540496} &:= (9 + 6 + 9 + 475 + 4 + 049 + 6)^4 \\
 &:= (9 + 6 + 9 + 475 + 40 + 4 + 9 + 6)^4 &= (9 + 6 + 94 + 7 - 54 + 0496)^4 \\
 & &= (96 + 947 - 540 + 49 + 6)^4 \\
 \\
 \mathbf{97644375361} &:= (9 + 7 + 64 + 43 + 75 + 361)^4 \\
 &:= (9 + 7 + 64 + 437 + 5 + 36 + 1)^4 \\
 &:= (97 + 6 + 4 + 437 + 5 + 3 + 6 + 1)^4 \\
 &:= (97 + 6 + 44 + 375 + 36 + 1)^4 &= (9 + 7 + 6 - 4 - 4 + 3 + 7 + 536 - 1)^4 \\
 & &= (97 - 6 + 443 - 7 - 5 + 36 + 1)^4 \\
 & &= (976 - 44 - 375 - 3 + 6 - 1)^4 \\
 & &= (-97 - 8 - 4 + 4723 - 7 - 1 + 2)^3 \\
 \\
 \mathbf{97844723712} &:= (9 + 78 + 4472 + 37 + 12)^3 \\
 \\
 \mathbf{99757432336} &:= (9 + 97 + 5 + 7 + 432 + 3 + 3 + 6)^4 \\
 &:= (99 + 7 + 5 + 7 + 432 + 3 + 3 + 6)^4 \\
 &:= (99 + 75 + 7 + 43 + 2 + 336)^4 &= (9 + 97 + 57 + 432 + 3 - 36)^4 \\
 & &= (99 + 75 + 74 + 323 - 3 - 6)^4 \\
 & &= (-99 + 757 - 432 + 336)^4
 \end{aligned}$$

7 All Semi-Selfie Numbers: Up To 11 Digits

Below are all up to 11-digits **semi-selfie numbers**. These are divided by subsections.

7.1 2-Digits Semi-Selfie Numbers

$$\mathbf{64} := (6 - 4)^6$$

$$\mathbf{81} := (8 + 1)^2$$

7.2 3-Digits Semi-Selfie Numbers

$$100 := (10 + 0)^2$$

$$121 := (12 - 1)^2$$

$$196 := (-1 + 9 + 6)^2$$

$$243 := (2 + 4 - 3)^5$$

$$512 := (5 - 1 - 2)^9$$

$$:= (5 + 1 + 2)^3$$

7.3 4-Digits Semi-Selfie Numbers

$$1000 := (10 + 00)^3$$

$$1024 := (10 - 2 - 4)^5$$

$$1296 := (1 + 2 + 9 - 6)^4$$
$$:= (1 + 29 + 6)^2$$

$$1331 := (13 - 3 + 1)^3$$

$$1728 := (-1 + 7 - 2 + 8)^3$$

$$1936 := (-1 + 9 + 36)^2$$

$$2025 := (20 + 25)^2$$

$$2048 := (-2 - 04 + 8)^{11}$$

$$2197 := (-2 - 1 + 9 + 7)^3$$

$$2401 := (2 + 4 + 01)^4$$

$$3025 := (30 + 25)^2$$
$$:= (3 - 1 - 2 + 5)^5$$

$$3125 := (-3 + 1 + 2 + 5)^5$$

$$3364 := (-3 - 3 + 64)^2$$

$$3969 := (3 - 9 + 69)^2$$

$$4913 := (4 + 9 + 1 + 3)^3$$

$$5776 := (5 + 77 - 6)^2$$

$$5832 := (5 + 8 + 3 + 2)^3$$

$$6084 := (-6 + 084)^2$$

$$6724 := (6 + 72 + 4)^2$$

$$7396 := (-7 - 3 + 96)^2$$

$$8192 := (8 + 1 - 9 + 2)^{13}$$
$$:= (-8 - 1 + 9 + 2)^{13}$$

$$8281 := (82 + 8 + 1)^2$$

$$:= (8 + 2 + 81)^2$$

$$9801 := (98 + 01)^2$$

7.4 5-Digits Semi-Selfie Numbers

$$10000 := (10 + 000)^4$$
$$:= (100 + 00)^2$$

$$10201 := (102 - 01)^2$$

$$11881 := (118 - 8 - 1)^2$$

$$12167 := (1 + 21 - 6 + 7)^3$$

$$12996 := (129 - 9 - 6)^2$$

$$14641 := (14 - 6 + 4 - 1)^4$$

$$15129 := (-1 - 5 + 129)^2$$

$$15625 := (1 + 5 + 6 - 2 - 5)^6$$
$$:= (1 - 5 + 6 - 2 + 5)^6$$

$$:= (-1 + 5 - 6 + 2 + 5)^6$$

$$:= (1 + 5 - 6 + 25)^3$$

$$:= (-1 - 5 + 6 + 25)^3$$

$$16384 := (1 - 6 + 3 + 8 - 4)^{14}$$

$$:= (-1 + 6 + 3 - 8 + 4)^7$$

$$:= (-1 - 6 - 3 + 8 + 4)^{14}$$

$$:= (1 - 6 - 3 + 8 + 4)^7$$

$$17161 := (-1 + 71 + 61)^2$$

$$17576 := (1 + 7 + 5 + 7 + 6)^3$$

$$17956 := (-1 + 79 + 56)^2$$

$$19683 := (-1 + 9 + 6 - 8 - 3)^9$$
$$:= (1 - 9 + 6 + 8 - 3)^9$$

$$:= (1 + 9 + 6 + 8 + 3)^3$$

$$20736 := (2 + 07 - 3 + 6)^4$$

$$21952 := (2 + 19 + 5 + 2)^3$$

$$32768 := (-3 + 2 + 7 - 6 + 8)^5$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 & := (-3 - 2 - 7 + 6 + 8)^{15} \\
 & := (3 - 2 - 7 + 6 + 8)^5 \\
 & := (3 + 27 - 6 + 8)^3 \\
 \mathbf{38416} & := (-3 + 8 + 4 - 1 + 6)^4 \\
 & := (3 + 8 - 4 + 1 + 6)^4 \\
 \mathbf{39204} & := (3 - 9 + 204)^2 \\
 \mathbf{46225} & := (-4 - 6 + 225)^2 \\
 \mathbf{46656} & := (-4 + 66 - 56)^6 \\
 \mathbf{54872} & := (-5 + 48 - 7 + 2)^3 \\
 \mathbf{55225} & := (5 + 5 + 225)^2 \\
 \mathbf{59049} & := (5 + 9 + 04 - 9)^5 \\
 & := (-5 + 9 - 04 + 9)^5 \\
 & := (5 - 9 + 04 + 9)^5 \\
 \mathbf{78125} & := (-7 + 8 + 1 - 2 + 5)^7 \\
 & := (7 - 8 - 1 + 2 + 5)^7 \\
 \mathbf{82369} & := (-82 + 369)^2 \\
 \mathbf{83521} & := (8 + 3 + 5 + 2 - 1)^4 \\
 \mathbf{88209} & := (88 + 209)^2 \\
 \mathbf{91125} & := (9 + 11 + 25)^3 \\
 \mathbf{97336} & := (9 + 73 - 36)^3
 \end{aligned}$$

7.5 6-Digits Semi-Selfie Numbers

$$\begin{aligned}
 \mathbf{100000} & := (10 + 0000)^5 \\
 \mathbf{103823} & := (10 + 38 + 2 - 3)^3 \\
 \mathbf{104329} & := (-10 + 4 + 329)^2 \\
 \mathbf{104976} & := (10 + 4 - 9 + 7 + 6)^4 \\
 \mathbf{110592} & := (1 - 10 + 59 - 2)^3 \\
 \mathbf{117649} & := (11 + 7 - 6 + 4 - 9)^6 \\
 & := (-11 + 7 + 6 - 4 + 9)^6 \\
 & := (1 + 17 - 6 + 4 - 9)^6 \\
 \mathbf{118336} & := (1 - 1 + 8 + 336)^2 \\
 & := (-1 + 1 + 8 + 336)^2 \\
 \mathbf{130321} & := (13 + 03 + 2 + 1)^4 \\
 \mathbf{131072} & := (1 - 3 - 1 + 07 - 2)^{17} \\
 & := (-1 - 3 + 1 + 07 - 2)^{17} \\
 & := (-13 + 10 + 7 - 2)^{17} \\
 \mathbf{132496} & := (-132 + 496)^2 \\
 \mathbf{132651} & := (1 + 3 + 2 - 6 + 51)^3 \\
 & := (-1 - 3 - 2 + 6 + 51)^3 \\
 & := (-13 - 2 + 65 + 1)^3 \\
 \mathbf{136161} & := (1 + 361 + 6 + 1)^2 \\
 \mathbf{136900} & := (1 + 369 + 00)^2 \\
 \mathbf{138384} & := (1 + 383 - 8 - 4)^2 \\
 & := (-1 - 3 - 8 + 384)^2 \\
 \mathbf{143641} & := (14 + 364 + 1)^2 \\
 \mathbf{148877} & := (-1 + 48 - 8 + 7 + 7)^3 \\
 \mathbf{157464} & := (-1 + 57 - 4 + 6 - 4)^3 \\
 \mathbf{161051} & := (16 + 1 - 05 - 1)^5 \\
 & := (16 - 1 - 05 + 1)^5 \\
 & := (1 + 6 + 10 - 5 - 1)^5 \\
 & := (-1 + 6 + 10 - 5 + 1)^5 \\
 & := (1 - 6 + 10 + 5 + 1)^5 \\
 & := (1 + 61 - 051)^5 \\
 \mathbf{166375} & := (1 + 6 + 6 + 37 + 5)^3 \\
 \mathbf{171396} & := (17 + 1 + 396)^2 \\
 \mathbf{175616} & := (-1 + 7 - 5 + 61 - 6)^3 \\
 & := (1 - 7 - 5 + 61 + 6)^3 \\
 \mathbf{177147} & := (1 + 7 + 7 - 1 - 4 - 7)^{11} \\
 & := (-1 + 7 + 7 + 1 - 4 - 7)^{11} \\
 & := (1 + 7 - 7 - 1 - 4 + 7)^{11} \\
 & := (1 - 7 + 7 - 1 - 4 + 7)^{11} \\
 & := (-1 + 7 - 7 + 1 - 4 + 7)^{11} \\
 & := (-1 - 7 + 7 + 1 - 4 + 7)^{11} \\
 & := (17 + 7 - 14 - 7)^{11} \\
 & := (17 - 7 - 14 + 7)^{11} \\
 \mathbf{185193} & := (18 + 51 - 9 - 3)^3 \\
 \mathbf{194481} & := (1 - 9 + 448 + 1)^2 \\
 \mathbf{195112} & := (1 + 9 + 51 - 1 - 2)^3 \\
 & := (-1 + 9 + 51 + 1 - 2)^3 \\
 & := (19 + 51 - 12)^3
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 \mathbf{213444} &:= (21 - 3 + 444)^2 & &:= (-3 + 7 - 1 - 2 + 9 + 3)^5 \\
 \mathbf{234256} &:= (2 + 3 + 4 + 2 + 5 + 6)^4 & &:= (37 - 12 - 9 - 3)^5 \\
 &:= (23 - 4 + 2 - 5 + 6)^4 & \mathbf{373248} &:= (-3 + 73 - 2 - 4 + 8)^3 \\
 &:= (2 - 3 + 4 + 25 - 6)^4 & &:= (37 + 3 + 24 + 8)^3 \\
 &:= (-2 - 3 - 4 + 25 + 6)^4 & \mathbf{389017} &:= (-3 - 8 + 90 + 1 - 7)^3 \\
 &:= (2 - 34 - 2 + 56)^4 & \mathbf{390625} &:= (-3 + 9 + 06 - 2 - 5)^8 \\
 &:= (-2 - 34 + 2 + 56)^4 & &:= (3 + 9 + 06 + 2 + 5)^4 \\
 &:= (-234 + 256)^4 & &:= (-3 + 9 - 06 + 25)^4 \\
 & & &:= (3 - 9 + 06 + 25)^4 \\
 \mathbf{238328} &:= (23 + 8 + 3 + 28)^3 & \mathbf{421875} &:= (-4 - 2 - 1 + 87 - 5)^3 \\
 \mathbf{245025} &:= (2 - 4 + 502 - 5)^2 & &:= (4 - 21 + 87 + 5)^3 \\
 \mathbf{250047} &:= (2 + 50 + 04 + 7)^3 & \mathbf{431649} &:= (4 + 3 + 1 + 649)^2 \\
 \mathbf{262144} &:= (2 - 6 - 2 + 14 - 4)^9 & \mathbf{438976} &:= (-4 - 3 - 8 + 97 - 6)^3 \\
 &:= (-2 - 6 + 2 + 14 - 4)^9 & &:= (4 - 3 + 8 - 9 + 76)^3 \\
 &:= (2 - 6 + 2 + 14 - 4)^6 & &:= (-4 + 3 - 8 + 9 + 76)^3 \\
 &:= (-2 - 6 - 2 + 14 + 4)^6 & \mathbf{455625} &:= (45 + 5 + 625)^2 \\
 \mathbf{273529} &:= (-2 - 7 + 3 + 529)^2 & \mathbf{456533} &:= (45 - 6 + 5 + 33)^3 \\
 \mathbf{279841} &:= (2 + 7 + 9 + 8 - 4 + 1)^4 & &:= (45 + 65 - 33)^3 \\
 &:= (27 + 9 - 8 - 4 - 1)^4 & &:= (-456 + 533)^3 \\
 &:= (27 - 9 + 8 - 4 + 1)^4 & \mathbf{469225} &:= (-4 + 692 + 2 - 5)^2 \\
 \mathbf{279936} &:= (2 + 7 + 9 - 9 + 3 - 6)^7 & \mathbf{470596} &:= (-4 + 705 - 9 - 6)^2 \\
 &:= (2 + 7 - 9 + 9 + 3 - 6)^7 & \mathbf{474552} &:= (-4 + 74 + 5 + 5 - 2)^3 \\
 &:= (-2 - 7 + 9 + 9 + 3 - 6)^7 & &:= (-474 + 552)^3 \\
 &:= (27 - 9 - 9 + 3 - 6)^7 & \mathbf{494209} &:= (494 + 209)^2 \\
 &:= (-2 - 79 + 93 - 6)^7 & \mathbf{531441} &:= (5 + 31 - 4 - 4 - 1)^4 \\
 \mathbf{287496} &:= (-2 + 87 - 4 - 9 - 6)^3 & &:= (-5 + 31 + 4 - 4 + 1)^4 \\
 \mathbf{300763} &:= (-3 + 007 + 63)^3 & &:= (-5 + 31 - 4 + 4 + 1)^4 \\
 \mathbf{314432} &:= (31 - 4 + 43 - 2)^3 & &:= (-5 - 3 + 14 + 4 - 1)^6 \\
 \mathbf{326041} &:= (-32 + 604 - 1)^2 & &:= (-5 - 3 + 14 - 4 + 1)^{12} \\
 \mathbf{331776} &:= (33 - 1 - 7 - 7 + 6)^4 & &:= (-5 + 3 + 14 - 4 + 1)^6 \\
 &:= (3 + 3 + 17 + 7 - 6)^4 & &:= (5 + 3 + 14 + 4 + 1)^4 \\
 &:= (-3 - 3 + 17 + 7 + 6)^4 & &:= (53 + 1 - 44 - 1)^6 \\
 \mathbf{357911} &:= (3 + 57 + 9 + 1 + 1)^3 & &:= (53 - 1 - 44 + 1)^6 \\
 &:= (-3 - 5 + 79 + 1 - 1)^3 & &:= (53 + 1 - 4 - 41)^6 \\
 &:= (-3 - 5 + 79 - 1 + 1)^3 & &:= (-5 - 31 + 44 + 1)^6 \\
 \mathbf{363609} &:= (3 - 6 - 3 + 609)^2 & &:= (5 + 31 + 44 + 1)^3 \\
 &:= (-3 - 6 + 3 + 609)^2 & &:= (-5 - 31 + 4 + 41)^6 \\
 \mathbf{371293} &:= (3 + 7 - 1 - 2 + 9 - 3)^5 & &:= (5 + 31 + 4 + 41)^3 \\
 &:= (-3 + 7 + 1 + 2 + 9 - 3)^5 & &
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 \mathbf{537824} &:= (53 - 7 - 8 - 24)^5 & & := (8 - 2 - 3 + 5 - 4 + 3)^7 \\
 \mathbf{551368} &:= (5 + 5 + 1 + 3 + 68)^3 & & := (-8 - 23 - 5 + 43)^7 \\
 &:= (55 + 13 + 6 + 8)^3 & & \mathbf{826281} := (826 + 2 + 81)^2 \\
 &:= (55 - 1 + 36 - 8)^3 & & \mathbf{829921} := (-82 + 992 + 1)^2 \\
 \mathbf{571536} &:= (5 + 715 + 36)^2 & & \mathbf{830584} := (8 - 3 + 05 + 84)^3 \\
 \mathbf{571787} &:= (-5 + 7 + 1 - 7 + 87)^3 & & \mathbf{839056} := (8 - 3 + 905 + 6)^2 \\
 &:= (-5 - 7 + 1 + 7 + 87)^3 & & \mathbf{842724} := (842 + 72 + 4)^2 \\
 \mathbf{592704} &:= (-5 + 92 - 7 + 04)^3 & & \mathbf{853776} := (853 + 77 - 6)^2 \\
 \mathbf{608400} &:= (-60 + 840 + 0)^2 & & \mathbf{877969} := (877 - 9 + 69)^2 \\
 \mathbf{614656} &:= (6 + 1 + 4 + 6 + 5 + 6)^4 & & \mathbf{884736} := (88 + 4 + 7 + 3 - 6)^3 \\
 &:= (-6 - 1 + 46 - 5 - 6)^4 & & & := (8 + 84 + 7 + 3 - 6)^3 \\
 \mathbf{627264} &:= (62 + 726 + 4)^2 & & \mathbf{893025} := (8 + 930 + 2 + 5)^2 \\
 \mathbf{636056} &:= (-6 + 36 + 056)^3 & & \mathbf{894916} := (-8 + 949 - 1 + 6)^2 \\
 \mathbf{644809} &:= (-6 + 4 - 4 + 809)^2 & & \mathbf{912673} := (91 + 2 - 6 + 7 + 3)^3 \\
 &:= (-6 - 4 + 4 + 809)^2 & & \mathbf{919681} := (-9 + 1 + 968 - 1)^2 \\
 & & & & := (-9 - 1 + 968 + 1)^2 \\
 \mathbf{648025} &:= (-6 + 4 + 802 + 5)^2 & & \mathbf{923521} := (-9 + 2 + 35 + 2 + 1)^4 \\
 \mathbf{658503} &:= (-6 + 5 + 85 + 03)^3 & & \mathbf{929296} := (929 + 29 + 6)^2 \\
 \mathbf{678976} &:= (-67 + 897 - 6)^2 & & \mathbf{941192} := (94 + 11 - 9 + 2)^3 \\
 \mathbf{680625} &:= (-6 + 806 + 25)^2 & & & := (-9 + 4 + 11 + 92)^3 \\
 \mathbf{681472} &:= (6 + 81 - 4 + 7 - 2)^3 & & \mathbf{970299} := (97 + 02 + 9 - 9)^3 \\
 &:= (-6 + 81 + 4 + 7 + 2)^3 & & & := (97 + 02 - 9 + 9)^3 \\
 &:= (-6 + 8 + 14 + 72)^3 & & & := (9 + 70 + 2 + 9 + 9)^3 \\
 \mathbf{704969} &:= (7 + 04 + 9 + 69)^3 & & & := (9 - 7 - 02 + 99)^3 \\
 \mathbf{707281} &:= (7 - 07 + 28 + 1)^4 & & & := (-9 + 7 + 02 + 99)^3 \\
 &:= (-7 + 07 + 28 + 1)^4 & & & := (9 + 70 + 29 - 9)^3 \\
 \mathbf{753571} &:= (75 + 3 + 5 + 7 + 1)^3 & & & := (-9 + 70 + 29 + 9)^3 \\
 &:= (7 + 5 + 3 + 5 + 71)^3 & & & \mathbf{972196} := (972 - 1 + 9 + 6)^2 \\
 \mathbf{763876} &:= (7 - 6 - 3 + 876)^2 & & & \mathbf{978121} := (978 + 12 - 1)^2 \\
 \mathbf{790321} &:= (7 + 903 - 21)^2 & & & \mathbf{980100} := (980 + 10 + 0)^2 \\
 \mathbf{804357} &:= (80 + 4 - 3 + 5 + 7)^3 & & & \mathbf{982081} := (982 + 08 + 1)^2 \\
 \mathbf{808201} &:= (80 + 820 - 1)^2 & & & \mathbf{998001} := (998 + 001)^2 \\
 \mathbf{823543} &:= (8 - 2 + 3 + 5 - 4 - 3)^7 & & & \\
 &:= (8 + 2 + 3 - 5 - 4 + 3)^7 & & &
 \end{aligned}$$

7.6 7-Digits Semi-Selfie Numbers

$$\begin{aligned}
 \mathbf{1000000} &:= (10 + 00000)^6 & & := (1000 + 000)^2 \\
 &:= (100 + 0000)^3 & & \mathbf{1002001} := (1002 - 001)^2
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 \mathbf{1018081} &:= (1018 - 08 - 1)^2 & & := (1 + 25 + 9 + 71 + 2)^3 \\
 \mathbf{1020100} &:= (1020 - 10 + 0)^2 & \mathbf{1261129} &:= (-12 + 6 + 1129)^2 \\
 \mathbf{1022121} &:= (1022 - 12 + 1)^2 & \mathbf{1295029} &:= (1 + 2 + 95 + 02 + 9)^3 \\
 \mathbf{1028196} &:= (1028 + 1 - 9 - 6)^2 & & := (1 + 29 + 50 + 29)^3 \\
 \mathbf{1030301} &:= (103 - 03 + 01)^3 & \mathbf{1331000} &:= (13 - 3 + 100 + 0)^3 \\
 \mathbf{1048576} &:= (10 + 4 + 8 - 5 - 7 - 6)^{10} & \mathbf{1336336} &:= (13 + 3 + 6 + 3 + 3 + 6)^4 \\
 &:= (10 + 4 - 8 - 5 + 7 - 6)^{20} & & := (1 + 33 + 6 + 3 - 3 - 6)^4 \\
 &:= (10 - 4 - 8 + 5 + 7 - 6)^{10} & & := (1 + 33 + 6 - 3 + 3 - 6)^4 \\
 &:= (10 + 4 + 8 - 5 - 7 + 6)^5 & & := (1 + 33 - 6 + 3 - 3 + 6)^4 \\
 &:= (10 - 4 - 8 + 5 - 7 + 6)^{20} & & := (1 + 33 - 6 - 3 + 3 + 6)^4 \\
 &:= (-10 - 4 + 8 - 5 + 7 + 6)^{20} & & := (1 + 3 + 36 + 3 - 3 - 6)^4 \\
 &:= (10 - 4 - 8 + 5 + 7 + 6)^5 & & := (1 + 3 + 36 - 3 + 3 - 6)^4 \\
 &:= (-10 + 4 - 8 + 5 + 7 + 6)^{10} & & := (1 - 3 + 36 + 3 + 3 - 6)^4 \\
 &:= (10 - 4 + 8 + 5 + 7 + 6)^4 & & := (1 - 3 + 36 - 3 - 3 + 6)^4 \\
 &:= (-10 + 48 - 5 - 7 + 6)^4 & & := (1 + 3 - 3 + 6 + 33 - 6)^4 \\
 &:= (-1 - 048 + 57 - 6)^{20} & & := (1 - 3 + 3 + 6 + 33 - 6)^4 \\
 &:= (1 - 048 + 57 - 6)^{10} & & := (1 + 3 - 3 - 6 + 33 + 6)^4 \\
 &:= (1 - 048 + 57 + 6)^5 & & := (1 - 3 + 3 - 6 + 33 + 6)^4 \\
 &:= (-1 - 048 + 5 + 76)^4 & & := (1 + 3 + 3 - 6 - 3 + 36)^4 \\
 &:= (-1 - 04 + 85 - 76)^{10} & & := (1 - 3 - 3 + 6 - 3 + 36)^4 \\
 &:= (104 - 85 + 7 + 6)^4 & & := (1 + 3 - 3 - 6 + 3 + 36)^4 \\
 & & & := (1 - 3 + 3 - 6 + 3 + 36)^4 \\
 \mathbf{1061208} &:= (106 - 12 + 08)^3 & & := (1 - 33 + 63 - 3 + 6)^4 \\
 \mathbf{1089936} &:= (1089 - 9 - 36)^2 & & := (1 + 3 + 3 + 63 - 36)^4 \\
 \mathbf{1092727} &:= (-1 + 092 + 7 - 2 + 7)^3 & & := (133 - 63 - 36)^4 \\
 \mathbf{1119364} &:= (1119 + 3 - 64)^2 & \mathbf{1367631} &:= (1 + 36 + 76 - 3 + 1)^3 \\
 & & & := (1 - 3 + 6 + 76 + 31)^3 \\
 \mathbf{1124864} &:= (-1 - 1 + 24 + 86 - 4)^3 & \mathbf{1419857} &:= (-1 + 4 - 1 + 9 + 8 + 5 - 7)^5 \\
 & & & := (1 - 4 + 1 + 9 + 8 - 5 + 7)^5 \\
 \mathbf{1157625} &:= (115 - 7 - 6 - 2 + 5)^3 & & := (1 + 4 - 1 + 9 - 8 + 5 + 7)^5 \\
 \mathbf{1162084} &:= (1162 - 084)^2 & & := (-1 + 4 + 1 + 9 - 8 + 5 + 7)^5 \\
 \mathbf{1179396} &:= (1179 + 3 - 96)^2 & & := (1 + 4 + 1 - 9 + 8 + 5 + 7)^5 \\
 \mathbf{1185921} &:= (1 - 1 + 8 - 5 + 9 + 21)^4 & \mathbf{1442897} &:= (14 - 4 - 2 + 8 + 97)^3 \\
 &:= (-1 + 1 + 8 - 5 + 9 + 21)^4 & & \mathbf{1495729} &:= (-1 + 495 + 729)^2 \\
 \mathbf{1191016} &:= (1 + 1 + 9 + 101 - 6)^3 & \mathbf{1500625} &:= (-1 + 5 + 006 + 25)^4 \\
 \mathbf{1201216} &:= (-120 + 1216)^2 & \mathbf{1560896} &:= (1 + 5 + 6 + 08 + 96)^3 \\
 \mathbf{1225043} &:= (12 + 2 + 50 + 43)^3 & & := (15 + 6 + 089 + 6)^3 \\
 \mathbf{1229881} &:= (122 + 988 - 1)^2 & \mathbf{1594323} &:= (1 + 5 + 9 - 4 - 3 - 2 - 3)^{13} \\
 &:= (-1 + 229 + 881)^2 & & \\
 \mathbf{1259712} &:= (1 + 2 + 5 + 97 + 1 + 2)^3 & & \\
 &:= (125 - 9 - 7 + 1 - 2)^3 & &
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 &:= (-1-5+9+4-3+2-3)^{13} \\
 &:= (1-5+9-4+3+2-3)^{13} \\
 &:= (1+5-9+4+3+2-3)^{13} \\
 &:= (-1-5+9-4+3-2+3)^{13} \\
 &:= (-1+5-9+4+3-2+3)^{13} \\
 &:= (1-5+9-4-3+2+3)^{13} \\
 &:= (1+5-9+4-3+2+3)^{13} \\
 &:= (1-5-9-4-3+23)^{13} \\
 \mathbf{1656369} &:= (1656-369)^2 \\
 \mathbf{1679616} &:= (-1+6-7+9+6-1-6)^8 \\
 &:= (1+6+7-9+6+1-6)^8 \\
 &:= (-1+6-7+9-6-1+6)^8 \\
 &:= (-1-6-7+9+6-1+6)^8 \\
 &:= (1+6+7-9-6+1+6)^8 \\
 &:= (1-6+7-9+6+1+6)^8 \\
 &:= (1+6+7+9+6+1+6)^4 \\
 &:= (16+7-9+6+16)^4 \\
 &:= (1+679+616)^2 \\
 \mathbf{1771561} &:= (17+7-1-5-6-1)^6 \\
 &:= (17-7+1-5+6-1)^6 \\
 &:= (17-7+1+5-6+1)^6 \\
 &:= (17-7-1-5+6+1)^6 \\
 &:= (1+7-7+15-6+1)^6 \\
 &:= (1-7+7+15-6+1)^6 \\
 &:= (1+77-1-5-61)^6 \\
 &:= (-1+77+1-5-61)^6 \\
 &:= (-1+7+71-5-61)^6 \\
 &:= (1-7+71-5+61)^3 \\
 &:= (177+1-56-1)^3 \\
 &:= (177-1-56+1)^3 \\
 &:= (-1+771+561)^2 \\
 \mathbf{1779556} &:= (-1+779+556)^2 \\
 \mathbf{1860496} &:= (1860-496)^2 \\
 \mathbf{1874161} &:= (18+7+4+1+6+1)^4 \\
 &:= (1+8+7+4+16+1)^4 \\
 &:= (-18+7+41+6+1)^4 \\
 \mathbf{1889568} &:= (-18+8+9+5+6+8)^5 \\
 &:= (1-8+89-56-8)^5 \\
 \mathbf{1953125} &:= (19-5-3+1-2-5)^9 \\
 &:= (-1-9+5+3+12-5)^9 \\
 &:= (1+9+5-3-12+5)^9 \\
 &:= (-1-9-5+3+12+5)^9 \\
 &:= (-19-5+3+1+25)^9 \\
 &:= (1+95+3+1+25)^3 \\
 &:= (-1+9-5-3+125)^3 \\
 &:= (1-9+5+3+125)^3 \\
 \mathbf{2085136} &:= (-2-08+51+3-6)^4 \\
 &:= (-2+08-5+1+36)^4 \\
 \mathbf{2097152} &:= (-2+09+7+1-5-2)^7 \\
 &:= (-2+09-7-1+5-2)^{21} \\
 &:= (2-09+7-1+5-2)^{21} \\
 &:= (2+09-7+1+5-2)^7 \\
 &:= (2+09-7+1-5+2)^{21} \\
 &:= (-2-09+7-1+5+2)^{21} \\
 &:= (-2+09-7+1+5+2)^7 \\
 &:= (2-09+7+1+5+2)^7 \\
 &:= (20-9-7+1+5-2)^7 \\
 &:= (20-9-7+1-5+2)^{21} \\
 &:= (-20+9+7-1+5+2)^{21} \\
 &:= (-2-09+71-52)^7 \\
 &:= (-20+97-1+52)^3 \\
 &:= (-20+9+71-52)^7 \\
 \mathbf{2299968} &:= (22+99+9-6+8)^3 \\
 &:= (22+9+99-6+8)^3 \\
 &:= (2+29+99-6+8)^3 \\
 &:= (229-99-6+8)^3 \\
 &:= (229-9-96+8)^3 \\
 \mathbf{2313441} &:= (-2+31+3+4+4-1)^4 \\
 &:= (2+31-3+4+4+1)^4 \\
 &:= (-2+3+1+34+4-1)^4 \\
 &:= (-2+3-1+34+4+1)^4 \\
 &:= (2-3+1+34+4+1)^4 \\
 \mathbf{2406104} &:= (24+06+104)^3 \\
 \mathbf{2476099} &:= (2+4+7+6+09-9)^5 \\
 &:= (2+4+7+6-09+9)^5 \\
 &:= (-2+4-7+6+09+9)^5
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 &:= (24 + 7 + 6 - 09 - 9)^5 \\
 \mathbf{2515456} &:= (-2 - 5 + 154 - 5 - 6)^3 \\
 &:= (25 + 1 + 54 + 56)^3 \\
 \mathbf{2825761} &:= (2 - 8 - 2 - 5 - 7 + 61)^4 \\
 &:= (-2 - 8 + 2 - 5 - 7 + 61)^4 \\
 &:= (28 + 25 - 7 - 6 + 1)^4 \\
 \mathbf{2863288} &:= (28 - 6 + 32 + 88)^3 \\
 \mathbf{2896804} &:= (2 + 896 + 804)^2 \\
 \mathbf{2924207} &:= (2 + 92 + 42 + 07)^3 \\
 \mathbf{2985984} &:= (29 + 8 + 5 + 98 + 4)^3 \\
 &:= (2 + 98 + 5 - 9 - 84)^6 \\
 &:= (2 - 9 + 8 + 59 + 84)^3 \\
 &:= (29 + 85 - 98 - 4)^6 \\
 &:= (29 + 8 + 59 - 84)^6 \\
 \mathbf{3017169} &:= (30 + 1716 - 9)^2 \\
 \mathbf{3048625} &:= (30 + 48 + 62 + 5)^3 \\
 &:= (30 + 4 + 86 + 25)^3 \\
 \mathbf{3111696} &:= (31 + 1 + 1 + 6 + 9 - 6)^4 \\
 &:= (31 + 1 + 1 - 6 + 9 + 6)^4 \\
 &:= (-31 - 1 - 1 + 69 + 6)^4 \\
 \mathbf{3112136} &:= (-3 + 112 + 1 + 36)^3 \\
 &:= (-3 + 11 + 2 + 136)^3 \\
 &:= (-3 + 1 + 12 + 136)^3 \\
 \mathbf{3175524} &:= (3 + 1755 + 24)^2 \\
 \mathbf{3418801} &:= (3 + 41 + 8 - 8 - 01)^4 \\
 &:= (3 + 41 - 8 + 8 - 01)^4 \\
 &:= (34 + 18 - 8 - 01)^4 \\
 &:= (-3 - 41 + 88 - 01)^4 \\
 &:= (-3 - 41 + 8 + 80 - 1)^4 \\
 \mathbf{3511808} &:= (-35 - 1 + 180 + 8)^3 \\
 \mathbf{3581577} &:= (3 + 5 + 81 + 57 + 7)^3 \\
 &:= (3 + 58 + 15 + 77)^3 \\
 \mathbf{3652264} &:= (36 + 52 + 2 + 64)^3 \\
 &:= (-3 - 65 + 226 - 4)^3 \\
 &:= (3 + 65 + 22 + 64)^3 \\
 \mathbf{3723875} &:= (3 + 72 - 3 + 8 + 75)^3 \\
 &:= (-3 + 72 + 3 + 8 + 75)^3 \\
 &:= (3 - 723 + 875)^3 \\
 \mathbf{3748096} &:= (37 - 4 + 8 + 09 - 6)^4 \\
 &:= (-37 + 4 + 80 - 9 + 6)^4 \\
 &:= (3 - 7 - 48 + 096)^4 \\
 \mathbf{3751969} &:= (-37 + 5 + 1969)^2 \\
 \mathbf{3796416} &:= (-3 + 79 + 64 + 16)^3 \\
 \mathbf{4084101} &:= (4 - 084 + 101)^5 \\
 \mathbf{4100625} &:= (4 + 10 + 06 + 25)^4 \\
 \mathbf{4173281} &:= (4 + 1 + 73 + 2 + 81)^3 \\
 &:= (41 + 7 + 32 + 81)^3 \\
 \mathbf{4194304} &:= (-4 + 19 - 4 - 3 - 04)^{11} \\
 &:= (41 - 9 + 4 - 30 - 4)^{22} \\
 &:= (41 - 9 - 4 - 30 + 4)^{22} \\
 \mathbf{4477456} &:= (4 + 4 - 7 - 7 - 4 + 56)^4 \\
 &:= (4 - 4 - 7 - 7 + 4 + 56)^4 \\
 &:= (-4 + 4 - 7 - 7 + 4 + 56)^4 \\
 &:= (4 + 4 + 77 - 45 + 6)^4 \\
 \mathbf{4741632} &:= (4 + 7 - 4 + 163 - 2)^3 \\
 &:= (-4 + 7 + 4 + 163 - 2)^3 \\
 \mathbf{4782969} &:= (-4 + 7 + 8 - 2 + 9 - 6 - 9)^{14} \\
 &:= (4 + 7 + 8 + 2 - 9 + 6 - 9)^7 \\
 &:= (4 - 7 + 8 - 2 + 9 + 6 - 9)^7 \\
 &:= (-4 + 7 - 8 + 2 + 9 + 6 - 9)^{14} \\
 &:= (-4 + 7 + 8 - 2 - 9 - 6 + 9)^{14} \\
 &:= (4 - 7 - 8 + 2 + 9 - 6 + 9)^{14} \\
 &:= (-4 + 7 - 8 + 2 + 9 - 6 + 9)^7 \\
 &:= (4 - 7 + 8 - 2 - 9 + 6 + 9)^7 \\
 &:= (-4 + 7 - 8 + 2 - 9 + 6 + 9)^{14} \\
 &:= (-4 - 7 - 8 - 2 + 9 + 6 + 9)^{14} \\
 &:= (4 - 7 - 8 + 29 - 6 - 9)^{14} \\
 &:= (-4 + 7 - 8 + 29 - 6 - 9)^7 \\
 &:= (-47 - 8 - 2 - 9 + 69)^{14} \\
 &:= (-4 - 78 - 2 + 96 - 9)^{14} \\
 \mathbf{4826809} &:= (-4 + 8 + 2 + 6 - 8 + 09)^6 \\
 &:= (-4 + 8 - 2 - 6 + 8 + 09)^6 \\
 &:= (-4 - 8 + 2 + 6 + 8 + 09)^6 \\
 &:= (-4 + 8 + 26 - 8 - 09)^6 \\
 &:= (-4 - 8 + 26 + 8 - 09)^6 \\
 &:= (-48 + 2 + 68 - 09)^6
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 &:= (-4 + 82 + 6 - 80 + 9)^6 \\
 &:= (4 + 82 - 6 + 80 + 9)^3 \\
 &:= (-4 + 826 - 809)^6 \\
 \mathbf{4879681} &:= (48 - 7 + 9 + 6 - 8 - 1)^4 \\
 &:= (48 + 7 - 9 - 6 + 8 - 1)^4 \\
 &:= (48 - 7 - 9 + 6 + 8 + 1)^4 \\
 &:= (4 - 8 - 7 - 9 + 68 - 1)^4 \\
 &:= (-4 - 8 - 7 - 9 - 6 + 81)^4 \\
 \mathbf{4941729} &:= (494 + 1729)^2 \\
 \mathbf{5153632} &:= (5 + 15 - 3 + 6 - 3 + 2)^5 \\
 &:= (5 + 15 + 3 - 6 + 3 + 2)^5 \\
 &:= (-5 + 1 - 5 + 36 - 3 - 2)^5 \\
 &:= (5 - 1 - 5 - 3 - 6 + 32)^5 \\
 &:= (-5 - 1 + 5 - 3 - 6 + 32)^5 \\
 &:= (-51 + 5 + 3 + 63 + 2)^5 \\
 &:= (-51 + 5 + 36 + 32)^5 \\
 \mathbf{5177717} &:= (-5 + 177 + 7 + 1 - 7)^3 \\
 &:= (-5 + 177 - 7 + 1 + 7)^3 \\
 \mathbf{5308416} &:= (53 - 08 - 4 + 1 + 6)^4 \\
 \mathbf{5359375} &:= (5 - 3 + 5 + 93 + 75)^3 \\
 \mathbf{5451776} &:= (54 + 51 + 77 - 6)^3 \\
 \mathbf{5545233} &:= (-55 + 4 - 5 + 233)^3 \\
 \mathbf{5764801} &:= (5 - 7 + 6 - 4 + 8 - 01)^8 \\
 &:= (-5 + 7 - 6 + 4 + 8 - 01)^8 \\
 &:= (5 + 7 + 6 - 4 - 8 + 01)^8 \\
 &:= (-5 - 7 + 6 + 4 + 8 + 01)^8 \\
 \mathbf{5929741} &:= (-5 + 92 + 97 - 4 + 1)^3 \\
 &:= (5 + 92 + 9 + 74 + 1)^3 \\
 \mathbf{6436343} &:= (6 + 4 + 3 + 6 + 3 + 4 - 3)^5 \\
 &:= (6 + 4 + 3 + 6 - 3 + 4 + 3)^5 \\
 &:= (6 + 4 - 3 + 6 + 3 + 4 + 3)^5 \\
 \mathbf{6644672} &:= (66 + 44 + 6 + 72)^3 \\
 &:= (66 + 4 + 46 + 72)^3 \\
 &:= (6 + 64 + 46 + 72)^3 \\
 \mathbf{6751269} &:= (67 + 51 + 2 + 69)^3 \\
 &:= (67 + 5 + 126 - 9)^3 \\
 &:= (-6 - 75 + 1 + 269)^3 \\
 \mathbf{6765201} &:= (-6 - 7 + 65 - 2 + 01)^4 \\
 \mathbf{7268416} &:= (7 + 2684 - 1 + 6)^2 \\
 \mathbf{7311616} &:= (7 + 31 + 1 + 6 + 1 + 6)^4 \\
 &:= (-7 + 3 - 11 + 61 + 6)^4 \\
 &:= (73 - 11 + 6 - 16)^4 \\
 \mathbf{7441984} &:= (744 + 1984)^2 \\
 \mathbf{7529536} &:= (7 + 5 - 29 - 5 + 36)^6 \\
 &:= (7 - 5 - 29 + 5 + 36)^6 \\
 &:= (75 - 2 - 95 + 36)^6 \\
 &:= (7 - 52 + 95 - 36)^6 \\
 &:= (7 - 529 + 536)^6 \\
 \mathbf{7645373} &:= (76 + 45 + 3 + 73)^3 \\
 &:= (7 + 64 + 53 + 73)^3 \\
 \mathbf{7762392} &:= (77 + 6 + 23 + 92)^3 \\
 &:= (7 + 76 + 23 + 92)^3 \\
 \mathbf{7828804} &:= (-78 + 2880 - 4)^2 \\
 \mathbf{7880599} &:= (7 + 88 + 05 + 99)^3 \\
 &:= (7 + 8 + 80 + 5 + 99)^3 \\
 \mathbf{7890481} &:= (7 + 8 - 9 + 048 - 1)^4 \\
 &:= (-7 - 8 - 9 - 04 + 81)^4 \\
 \mathbf{7962624} &:= (7 + 9 + 6 + 2 + 6 - 2 - 4)^5 \\
 &:= (7 + 9 + 6 - 2 + 6 + 2 - 4)^5 \\
 &:= (7 + 9 + 6 + 2 - 6 + 2 + 4)^5 \\
 &:= (7 + 9 - 6 + 2 + 6 + 2 + 4)^5 \\
 &:= (7 - 9 + 6 + 26 - 2 - 4)^5 \\
 &:= (-7 + 9 - 6 + 26 - 2 + 4)^5 \\
 &:= (7 - 9 - 6 + 26 + 2 + 4)^5 \\
 &:= (-7 + 9 + 6 - 2 - 6 + 24)^5 \\
 &:= (7 - 9 + 6 + 2 - 6 + 24)^5 \\
 &:= (-7 + 9 - 6 - 2 + 6 + 24)^5 \\
 &:= (7 + 9 + 6 + 26 - 24)^5 \\
 \mathbf{8242408} &:= (8 + 242 - 40 - 8)^3 \\
 &:= (-8 + 242 - 40 + 8)^3 \\
 \mathbf{8388608} &:= (8 + 38 + 8 - 60 + 8)^{23} \\
 \mathbf{8503056} &:= (8 + 50 - 3 + 05 - 6)^4 \\
 &:= (8 + 5 + 030 + 5 + 6)^4 \\
 &:= (85 - 030 + 5 - 6)^4 \\
 \mathbf{8615125} &:= (86 - 1 - 5 + 125)^3
 \end{aligned}$$

$$8741816 := (8 + 7 + 4 + 181 + 6)^3$$

$$8869743 := (88 + 69 + 7 + 43)^3$$

$$8998912 := (8 + 99 + 8 + 91 + 2)^3$$

$$:= (8 + 9 + 98 + 91 + 2)^3$$

$$:= (89 + 98 + 9 + 12)^3$$

$$:= (8 + 99 + 89 + 12)^3$$

$$9129329 := (-91 + 293 - 2 + 9)^3$$

$$:= (-91 - 29 + 329)^3$$

$$:= (9 - 129 + 329)^3$$

$$9150625 := (9 - 1 + 50 - 6 - 2 + 5)^4$$

$$:= (-9 + 1 + 50 + 6 + 2 + 5)^4$$

$$:= (91 - 5 - 06 - 25)^4$$

$$:= (9 + 15 + 06 + 25)^4$$

$$9765625 := (-9 + 76 + 5 - 62 - 5)^{10}$$

$$:= (-9 + 76 - 5 - 62 + 5)^{10}$$

$$:= (9 - 76 + 5 + 62 + 5)^{10}$$

$$:= (-97 + 65 + 62 - 5)^5$$

$$9834496 := (98 - 3 + 4 - 49 + 6)^4$$

$$:= (9 - 8 + 3 - 44 + 96)^4$$

$$9938375 := (99 + 38 + 3 + 75)^3$$

7.7 8-Digits Semi-Selfie Numbers

$$10000000 := (10 + 000000)^7$$

$$10077696 := (1 + 007 + 7 + 6 - 9 - 6)^9$$

$$:= (1 + 007 + 7 - 6 - 9 + 6)^9$$

$$:= (-1 - 007 - 7 + 6 + 9 + 6)^9$$

$$:= (100 + 7 + 7 + 6 + 96)^3$$

$$10316944 := (-1 + 03169 + 44)^2$$

$$10793861 := (1079 + 3 - 861)^3$$

$$11239424 := (1 + 123 + 94 + 2 + 4)^3$$

$$11316496 := (1 + 1 + 31 + 6 + 4 + 9 + 6)^4$$

$$:= (11 - 3 + 1 + 64 - 9 - 6)^4$$

$$:= (-11 + 3 - 1 + 64 + 9 - 6)^4$$

$$:= (11 - 3 + 1 + 6 + 49 - 6)^4$$

$$:= (11 - 3 + 1 - 6 + 49 + 6)^4$$

$$:= (1 + 1 - 3 + 16 + 49 - 6)^4$$

$$11329956 := (11 + 3299 + 56)^2$$

$$11336689 := (1 + 1 + 3366 + 8 - 9)^2$$

$$:= (1 - 1 + 3366 - 8 + 9)^2$$

$$:= (-1 + 1 + 3366 - 8 + 9)^2$$

$$11390625 := (1 - 1 + 3 + 9 + 06 + 2 - 5)^6$$

$$:= (-1 + 1 + 3 + 9 + 06 + 2 - 5)^6$$

$$:= (1 - 1 - 3 + 9 + 06 - 2 + 5)^6$$

$$:= (-1 + 1 - 3 + 9 + 06 - 2 + 5)^6$$

$$:= (1 + 1 + 3 + 9 - 06 + 2 + 5)^6$$

$$:= (1 + 1 + 3 - 9 - 06 + 25)^6$$

$$:= (-11 + 39 - 06 - 2 - 5)^6$$

$$:= (-11 + 3 + 90 - 62 - 5)^6$$

$$11543176 := (1 + 1 + 5 + 43 + 176)^3$$

$$11543176 := (115 + 4 + 31 + 76)^3$$

$$11697083 := (-1 + 169 + 70 - 8 - 3)^3$$

$$11852352 := (-1 - 1 - 8 + 5 + 235 - 2)^3$$

$$11881376 := (11 + 8 + 8 + 1 - 3 + 7 - 6)^5$$

$$:= (11 + 8 - 8 - 1 + 3 + 7 + 6)^5$$

$$:= (11 - 8 + 8 - 1 + 3 + 7 + 6)^5$$

$$:= (1 + 18 + 8 + 1 - 3 + 7 - 6)^5$$

$$:= (-1 + 18 + 8 - 1 + 3 - 7 + 6)^5$$

$$:= (1 + 18 - 8 - 1 + 3 + 7 + 6)^5$$

$$:= (-1 + 18 - 8 + 1 + 3 + 7 + 6)^5$$

$$:= (-1 - 1 + 8 + 8 + 13 - 7 + 6)^5$$

$$:= (1 - 1 + 8 - 8 + 13 + 7 + 6)^5$$

$$:= (-1 + 1 + 8 - 8 + 13 + 7 + 6)^5$$

$$:= (1 - 1 - 8 + 8 + 13 + 7 + 6)^5$$

$$:= (-1 + 1 - 8 + 8 + 13 + 7 + 6)^5$$

$$:= (1 - 1 - 8 - 8 - 1 + 37 + 6)^5$$

$$:= (-1 + 1 - 8 - 8 - 1 + 37 + 6)^5$$

$$:= (-1 - 1 - 8 - 8 + 1 + 37 + 6)^5$$

$$12117361 := (-12 + 1 - 1 + 7 + 3 + 61)^4$$

$$:= (-12 - 1 + 1 + 7 + 3 + 61)^4$$

$$:= (1 - 21 + 1 + 73 + 6 - 1)^4$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 &:= (1 - 21 - 1 + 73 + 6 + 1)^4 & &:= (-1 - 3 + 8 - 4 + 58 + 4 - 1)^4 \\
 &:= (-1 - 21 + 1 + 73 + 6 + 1)^4 & &:= (1 + 3 - 8 + 4 + 58 + 4 - 1)^4 \\
 &:= (-1 - 2 + 11 - 7 - 3 + 61)^4 & &:= (-1 + 3 + 8 - 4 + 58 - 4 + 1)^4 \\
 &:= (1 - 2 - 11 + 7 + 3 + 61)^4 & &:= (-1 + 3 - 8 + 4 + 58 + 4 + 1)^4 \\
 &:= (-1 - 21 + 17 + 3 + 61)^4 & &:= (-13 + 84 - 5 - 8 + 4 - 1)^4 \\
 &:= (-121 + 173 + 6 + 1)^4 & &:= (13 + 8 + 45 - 8 + 4 - 1)^4 \\
 \mathbf{12326391} &:= (1 - 23 + 263 - 9 - 1)^3 & &:= (13 - 8 + 45 + 8 + 4 - 1)^4 \\
 &:= (-1 - 23 + 263 - 9 + 1)^3 & &:= (-13 - 8 + 4 - 5 + 84 - 1)^4 \\
 &:= (1 - 2 + 326 - 3 - 91)^3 & &:= (13 + 8 - 4 - 5 + 8 + 41)^4 \\
 &:= (-123 + 263 + 91)^3 & &:= (-1 + 38 - 4 - 5 - 8 + 41)^4 \\
 \mathbf{12355225} &:= (-12 + 3552 - 25)^2 & &:= (13 + 8 - 45 + 84 + 1)^4 \\
 \mathbf{12487168} &:= (1 + 248 + 7 - 16 - 8)^3 & & \mathbf{14172488} := (141 + 7 + 2 + 4 + 88)^3 \\
 &:= (-1 + 248 - 7 - 16 + 8)^3 & &:= (-1 + 4 - 17 + 248 + 8)^3 \\
 &:= (1 - 24 + 87 + 168)^3 & &:= (14 + 172 + 48 + 8)^3 \\
 \mathbf{12649337} &:= (126 + 4 + 93 + 3 + 7)^3 & &:= (-14 + 172 - 4 + 88)^3 \\
 \mathbf{12812904} &:= (128 + 12 + 90 + 4)^3 & & \mathbf{14348907} := (-14 + 3 + 4 + 8 + 9 - 07)^{15} \\
 \mathbf{12977875} &:= (129 + 7 + 7 + 87 + 5)^3 & &:= (14 + 3 - 4 - 8 - 9 + 07)^{15} \\
 \mathbf{13144256} &:= (-13 + 1 - 4 - 4 + 256)^3 & &:= (14 + 3 + 4 + 8 - 9 + 07)^5 \\
 &:= (1 - 3 - 14 - 4 + 256)^3 & &:= (-14 - 3 - 4 + 8 + 9 + 07)^{15} \\
 \mathbf{13293316} &:= (1 + 329 + 3316)^2 & &:= (-1 + 4 + 34 - 8 - 9 + 07)^5 \\
 \mathbf{13312053} &:= (1 + 33 + 1 + 205 - 3)^3 & &:= (-1 - 43 - 4 - 8 + 90 - 7)^5 \\
 &:= (1 + 3 + 31 + 205 - 3)^3 & &:= (-1 - 4 - 3 - 48 + 90 - 7)^5 \\
 &:= (1 - 3 + 31 + 205 + 3)^3 & &:= (143 + 4 + 89 + 07)^3 \\
 \mathbf{13366336} &:= (-1 + 3 + 3663 - 3 - 6)^2 & &:= (-14 - 34 - 8 + 90 - 7)^5 \\
 &:= (-1 - 3 + 3663 + 3 - 6)^2 & & \mathbf{14526784} := (145 + 2 + 6 + 7 + 84)^3 \\
 \mathbf{13373649} &:= (1 + 3 - 3 + 7 + 3649)^2 & &:= (-14 - 5 + 267 - 8 + 4)^3 \\
 &:= (1 - 3 + 3 + 7 + 3649)^2 & &:= (-14 - 526 + 784)^3 \\
 \mathbf{13481272} &:= (13 - 48 + 1 + 272)^3 & & \mathbf{14737921} := (1 + 47 + 3792 - 1)^2 \\
 \mathbf{13557124} &:= (1 + 3557 + 124)^2 & &:= (-1 + 47 + 3792 + 1)^2 \\
 \mathbf{13586596} &:= (-1 + 3586 + 5 + 96)^2 & & \mathbf{14776336} := (-1 + 4 + 77 - 6 - 3 - 3 - 6)^4 \\
 \mathbf{13660416} &:= (1 + 3660 + 41 - 6)^2 & &:= (1 - 4 + 77 - 6 + 3 - 3 - 6)^4 \\
 \mathbf{13675204} &:= (-1 + 3675 + 20 + 4)^2 & &:= (1 - 4 + 77 - 6 - 3 + 3 - 6)^4 \\
 \mathbf{13697401} &:= (1 + 3697 + 4 - 01)^2 & &:= (1 + 4 - 7 + 76 - 3 - 3 - 6)^4 \\
 &:= (-1 + 3697 + 4 + 01)^2 & &:= (-1 + 4 + 7 + 7 + 6 + 33 + 6)^4 \\
 \mathbf{13786369} &:= (-1 + 3786 - 3 - 69)^2 & &:= (-1 + 4 + 7 + 7 + 6 + 3 + 36)^4 \\
 \mathbf{13845841} &:= (1 + 38 + 4 + 5 + 8 + 4 + 1)^4 & &:= (1 + 47 - 7 - 6 + 33 - 6)^4 \\
 &:= (1 + 3 + 8 - 4 + 58 - 4 - 1)^4 & & \mathbf{14886936} := (148 + 86 + 9 - 3 + 6)^3 \\
 &:= (-1 - 3 + 8 + 4 + 58 - 4 - 1)^4 & & \mathbf{14938225} := (-1 + 49 + 3822 - 5)^2
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 \mathbf{15038884} &:= (-1 - 5 + 03888 - 4)^2 && := (16 - 7 + 7 - 7 - 2 + 1 - 6)^{24} \\
 \mathbf{15069223} &:= (150 + 6 + 92 + 2 - 3)^3 && := (16 + 7 + 7 - 7 - 2 + 1 - 6)^6 \\
 \mathbf{15252992} &:= (-1 - 5 + 252 + 9 - 9 + 2)^3 && := (16 - 7 - 7 + 7 - 2 + 1 - 6)^{24} \\
 &:= (-1 - 5 + 252 - 9 + 9 + 2)^3 && := (16 + 7 - 7 + 7 - 2 + 1 - 6)^6 \\
 \mathbf{15438249} &:= (15 - 4 - 3 - 8 + 249)^3 && := (16 - 7 + 7 + 7 - 2 + 1 - 6)^6 \\
 &:= (-15 + 4 + 3 + 8 + 249)^3 && := (-16 + 7 + 7 + 7 + 2 + 1 - 6)^{24} \\
 \mathbf{15539364} &:= (15 - 5 + 3936 - 4)^2 && := (-16 + 7 + 7 + 7 - 2 - 1 + 6)^8 \\
 \mathbf{15625000} &:= (1 + 5 - 6 + 250 + 00)^3 && := (16 - 7 - 7 - 7 + 2 - 1 + 6)^{24} \\
 &:= (-1 - 5 + 6 + 250 + 00)^3 && := (16 + 7 - 7 - 7 + 2 - 1 + 6)^6 \\
 \mathbf{15752961} &:= (1 + 57 + 5 - 2 + 9 - 6 - 1)^4 && := (16 - 7 + 7 - 7 + 2 - 1 + 6)^6 \\
 &:= (-1 + 57 - 5 - 2 + 9 + 6 - 1)^4 && := (16 - 7 - 7 + 7 + 2 - 1 + 6)^6 \\
 &:= (-1 + 57 + 5 - 2 + 9 - 6 + 1)^4 && := (16 - 7 - 7 - 7 + 2 + 1 + 6)^{12} \\
 &:= (1 + 57 + 5 + 2 - 9 + 6 + 1)^4 && := (-1 + 6 + 7 + 7 + 7 - 2 - 16)^8 \\
 &:= (1 + 5 + 75 - 2 - 9 - 6 - 1)^4 && := (1 - 6 + 7 + 7 + 7 + 2 - 16)^{24} \\
 &:= (-1 - 5 + 75 - 2 - 9 + 6 - 1)^4 && := (1 - 6 + 7 - 7 - 7 - 2 + 16)^{24} \\
 &:= (-1 + 5 + 75 - 2 - 9 - 6 + 1)^4 && := (1 - 6 - 7 + 7 - 7 - 2 + 16)^{24} \\
 &:= (-1 + 5 - 7 + 52 + 9 + 6 - 1)^4 && := (1 - 6 + 7 + 7 - 7 - 2 + 16)^6 \\
 &:= (1 + 5 + 7 + 52 - 9 + 6 + 1)^4 && := (1 - 6 - 7 - 7 + 7 - 2 + 16)^{24} \\
 &:= (15 + 7 + 5 + 29 + 6 + 1)^4 && := (1 - 6 + 7 - 7 + 7 - 2 + 16)^6 \\
 &:= (15 - 7 + 5 - 2 - 9 + 61)^4 && := (1 - 6 - 7 + 7 + 7 - 2 + 16)^6 \\
 &:= (157 + 5 - 2 - 96 - 1)^4 && := (-1 + 6 - 7 - 7 - 7 + 2 + 16)^{24} \\
 &:= (-15 - 7 - 5 + 29 + 61)^4 && := (1 + 6 - 7 - 7 - 7 + 2 + 16)^{12} \\
 \mathbf{15813251} &:= (1 - 5 + 8 - 1 - 3 + 251)^3 && := (-1 - 6 + 7 - 7 - 7 + 2 + 16)^{12} \\
 &:= (-1 - 5 + 8 + 1 - 3 + 251)^3 && := (-1 + 6 + 7 - 7 - 7 + 2 + 16)^6 \\
 &:= (1 + 5 - 8 - 1 + 3 + 251)^3 && := (-1 - 6 - 7 + 7 - 7 + 2 + 16)^{12} \\
 &:= (-1 + 5 - 8 + 1 + 3 + 251)^3 && := (-1 + 6 - 7 + 7 - 7 + 2 + 16)^6 \\
 &:= (1 + 5 - 81 + 325 + 1)^3 && := (-1 - 6 - 7 - 7 + 7 + 2 + 16)^{12} \\
 \mathbf{15944049} &:= (-1 - 59 + 4 + 4049)^2 && := (-1 + 6 - 7 - 7 + 7 + 2 + 16)^6 \\
 \mathbf{16194277} &:= (161 + 94 - 2 + 7 - 7)^3 && := (16 + 7 + 7 - 7 - 21 + 6)^8 \\
 &:= (161 + 94 - 2 - 7 + 7)^3 && := (16 + 7 - 7 + 7 - 21 + 6)^8 \\
 &:= (161 + 9 + 4 + 2 + 77)^3 && := (16 - 7 + 7 + 7 - 21 + 6)^8 \\
 &:= (-16 + 194 - 2 + 77)^3 && := (-16 + 7 - 7 - 7 + 21 + 6)^{12} \\
 \mathbf{16540489} &:= (-1 + 6 + 5 + 4048 + 9)^2 && := (-16 - 7 + 7 - 7 + 21 + 6)^{12} \\
 \mathbf{16581375} &:= (165 + 81 - 3 + 7 + 5)^3 && := (-16 - 7 - 7 + 7 + 21 + 6)^{12} \\
 \mathbf{16777216} &:= (16 + 7 - 7 - 7 + 2 - 1 - 6)^{12} && := (16 + 7 + 7 + 7 + 21 + 6)^4 \\
 &:= (16 - 7 + 7 - 7 + 2 - 1 - 6)^{12} && := (1 - 67 + 77 - 2 - 1 - 6)^{24} \\
 &:= (16 - 7 - 7 + 7 + 2 - 1 - 6)^{12} && := (-1 - 67 + 77 + 2 - 1 - 6)^{12} \\
 &:= (16 + 7 - 7 - 7 - 2 + 1 - 6)^{24} && := (-1 - 67 + 77 - 2 + 1 - 6)^{24}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 &:= (1 - 67 + 77 - 2 + 1 - 6)^{12} \\
 &:= (1 - 67 + 77 + 2 + 1 - 6)^8 \\
 &:= (-1 - 67 + 77 + 2 - 1 + 6)^6 \\
 &:= (1 - 67 + 77 - 2 + 1 + 6)^6 \\
 &:= (-1 - 67 + 7 + 72 - 1 - 6)^{12} \\
 &:= (1 - 67 + 7 + 72 + 1 - 6)^8 \\
 &:= (1 + 67 + 7 - 72 - 1 + 6)^8 \\
 &:= (-1 - 67 - 7 + 72 - 1 + 6)^{24} \\
 &:= (1 - 67 - 7 + 72 - 1 + 6)^{12} \\
 &:= (-1 - 67 + 7 + 72 - 1 + 6)^6 \\
 &:= (-1 + 67 + 7 - 72 + 1 + 6)^8 \\
 &:= (-1 - 67 - 7 + 72 + 1 + 6)^{12} \\
 &:= (1 + 67 + 7 + 7 - 2 - 16)^4 \\
 &:= (1 + 6 + 77 + 7 - 21 - 6)^4 \\
 &:= (1 - 6 + 77 + 7 - 21 + 6)^4 \\
 &:= (1 + 6 + 7 + 77 - 21 - 6)^4 \\
 &:= (1 - 6 + 7 + 77 - 21 + 6)^4 \\
 &:= (16 - 77 + 72 - 1 - 6)^{12} \\
 &:= (16 + 77 - 72 + 1 - 6)^6 \\
 &:= (16 - 77 + 72 - 1 + 6)^6 \\
 &:= (-1 + 67 - 77 + 21 - 6)^{12} \\
 &:= (-1 + 67 - 77 + 21 + 6)^6 \\
 &:= (1 - 6 + 77 - 72 + 16)^6 \\
 &:= (-1 - 6 - 77 + 72 + 16)^{12} \\
 &:= (-1 + 6 - 77 + 72 + 16)^6 \\
 & \mathbf{17073424} := (1 + 707 + 3424)^2 \\
 & \mathbf{17210368} := (1 + 7 + 2 + 1 + 03 + 6 + 8)^5 \\
 &:= (-1 + 7 + 21 + 03 + 6 - 8)^5 \\
 &:= (1 + 7 + 21 - 03 - 6 + 8)^5 \\
 &:= (17 + 2 + 10 - 3 - 6 + 8)^5 \\
 &:= (-17 + 2 - 1 + 036 + 8)^5 \\
 &:= (1 + 72 - 1 - 036 - 8)^5 \\
 &:= (-1 + 72 + 1 - 036 - 8)^5 \\
 &:= (1 + 7 + 2 - 10 + 36 - 8)^5 \\
 &:= (-1 - 7 - 2 + 10 + 36 - 8)^5 \\
 &:= (-1 - 7 + 2 - 10 + 36 + 8)^5 \\
 &:= (-1 - 72 + 103 + 6 - 8)^5 \\
 & \mathbf{17373979} := (-1 - 7 + 373 - 97 - 9)^3 \\
 & \mathbf{17779581} := (177 + 7 - 9 + 5 + 81)^3 \\
 &:= (1 + 77 + 7 + 95 + 81)^3 \\
 &:= (1 + 7 + 77 + 95 + 81)^3 \\
 & \mathbf{17850625} := (1 + 78 - 5 - 06 + 2 - 5)^4 \\
 &:= (1 + 7 + 8 + 50 + 6 - 2 - 5)^4 \\
 &:= (-1 + 7 + 8 + 50 - 6 + 2 + 5)^4 \\
 &:= (1 - 7 + 8 + 50 + 6 + 2 + 5)^4 \\
 &:= (-17 + 85 - 06 - 2 + 5)^4 \\
 &:= (1 + 78 + 5 + 06 - 25)^4 \\
 &:= (-1 - 7 - 8 + 50 + 6 + 25)^4 \\
 & \mathbf{17984728} := (179 + 84 - 7 - 2 + 8)^3 \\
 &:= (179 + 8 + 47 + 28)^3 \\
 &:= (-1 + 7 + 984 - 728)^3 \\
 & \mathbf{18191447} := (-1 + 8 - 191 + 447)^3 \\
 & \mathbf{18429849} := (-18 + 4298 + 4 + 9)^2 \\
 & \mathbf{18974736} := (1 - 8 + 9 + 74 - 7 + 3 - 6)^4 \\
 &:= (-1 - 8 - 9 + 74 + 7 - 3 + 6)^4 \\
 &:= (1 - 8 + 9 - 7 + 4 + 73 - 6)^4 \\
 &:= (-1 + 8 - 9 - 7 - 4 + 73 + 6)^4 \\
 &:= (1 - 8 - 9 + 7 - 4 + 73 + 6)^4 \\
 &:= (18 - 9 + 7 + 47 - 3 + 6)^4 \\
 &:= (-1 + 8 + 97 - 47 + 3 + 6)^4 \\
 & \mathbf{19044496} := (-1 - 90 + 4449 + 6)^2 \\
 & \mathbf{19114384} := (-1 - 9 - 1 - 1 + 4384)^2 \\
 & \mathbf{19439281} := (1 + 9 + 4392 + 8 - 1)^2 \\
 &:= (-1 + 9 + 4392 + 8 + 1)^2 \\
 & \mathbf{19465109} := (194 + 65 + 1 + 09)^3 \\
 &:= (1 + 94 + 65 + 109)^3 \\
 & \mathbf{19487171} := (19 - 4 + 8 - 7 + 1 - 7 + 1)^7 \\
 &:= (1 + 9 + 4 + 8 + 7 - 17 - 1)^7 \\
 &:= (-1 - 9 + 4 + 8 - 7 + 17 - 1)^7 \\
 &:= (1 - 9 + 4 - 8 + 7 + 17 - 1)^7 \\
 &:= (-1 + 9 + 4 + 8 + 7 - 17 + 1)^7 \\
 &:= (-1 - 9 + 4 - 8 + 7 + 17 + 1)^7 \\
 &:= (-1 + 94 - 87 - 1 + 7 - 1)^7 \\
 &:= (1 - 9 + 4 + 87 - 1 - 71)^7 \\
 &:= (-1 - 9 + 4 + 87 + 1 - 71)^7 \\
 &:= (1 + 94 + 87 - 171)^7
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 \mathbf{19902511} &:= (1 + 9 + 9 + 0251 + 1)^3 \\
 \mathbf{20123648} &:= (201 + 2 - 3 + 64 + 8)^3 \\
 \mathbf{20151121} &:= (2 + 01 + 51 + 12 + 1)^4 \\
 &:= (-2 - 01 - 51 + 121)^4 \\
 &:= (20 + 15 + 11 + 21)^4 \\
 \mathbf{20511149} &:= (20 + 5 + 1 - 1 - 1 - 4 + 9)^5 \\
 &:= (20 + 5 - 1 + 1 - 1 - 4 + 9)^5 \\
 &:= (20 + 5 - 1 - 1 + 1 - 4 + 9)^5 \\
 &:= (20 - 5 + 1 + 1 - 1 + 4 + 9)^5 \\
 &:= (20 - 5 + 1 - 1 + 1 + 4 + 9)^5 \\
 &:= (20 - 5 - 1 + 1 + 1 + 4 + 9)^5 \\
 &:= (2 + 051 - 11 - 4 - 9)^5 \\
 &:= (2 + 051 - 1 - 14 - 9)^5 \\
 &:= (-20 + 51 + 11 - 4 - 9)^5 \\
 &:= (20 - 51 + 11 + 49)^5 \\
 \mathbf{20570824} &:= (20 - 570 + 824)^3 \\
 \mathbf{20796875} &:= (207 - 9 - 6 + 8 + 75)^3 \\
 \mathbf{21253933} &:= (21 + 253 + 9 - 3 - 3)^3 \\
 \mathbf{21381376} &:= (2 - 1 + 3 - 8 - 1 - 3 + 76)^4 \\
 &:= (-2 + 1 + 3 - 8 + 1 - 3 + 76)^4 \\
 &:= (2 - 1 - 3 - 8 - 1 + 3 + 76)^4 \\
 &:= (-2 + 1 - 3 - 8 + 1 + 3 + 76)^4 \\
 &:= (21 + 38 - 1 - 3 + 7 + 6)^4 \\
 &:= (21 - 3 + 8 - 1 + 37 + 6)^4 \\
 &:= (-21 + 3 + 8 - 1 + 3 + 76)^4 \\
 &:= (2 - 13 + 81 - 3 + 7 - 6)^4 \\
 &:= (-2 - 13 + 81 + 3 - 7 + 6)^4 \\
 &:= (21 - 3 + 81 - 37 + 6)^4 \\
 &:= (2 + 138 + 1 + 3 - 76)^4 \\
 \mathbf{21446161} &:= (2 + 14 + 4616 - 1)^2 \\
 \mathbf{21484952} &:= (214 + 8 + 49 + 5 + 2)^3 \\
 \mathbf{21594609} &:= (-21 + 59 + 4609)^2 \\
 \mathbf{21717639} &:= (217 + 1 + 7 + 63 - 9)^3 \\
 \mathbf{21717639} &:= (217 + 17 + 6 + 39)^3 \\
 \mathbf{22174681} &:= (22 - 1 + 7 + 4681)^2 \\
 \mathbf{22425768} &:= (224 + 2 - 5 - 7 + 68)^3 \\
 \mathbf{22477081} &:= (-22 + 4770 - 8 + 1)^2 \\
 \mathbf{22665187} &:= (-2 + 266 + 5 - 1 + 8 + 7)^3 \\
 \mathbf{22667121} &:= (2 - 2 + 66 + 7 - 1 - 2 - 1)^4 \\
 &:= (-2 + 2 + 66 + 7 - 1 - 2 - 1)^4 \\
 &:= (-2 - 2 + 66 + 7 - 1 + 2 - 1)^4 \\
 &:= (-2 - 2 + 66 + 7 + 1 - 2 + 1)^4 \\
 &:= (2 - 2 + 6 + 67 - 1 - 2 - 1)^4 \\
 &:= (-2 + 2 + 6 + 67 - 1 - 2 - 1)^4 \\
 &:= (-2 - 2 + 6 + 67 - 1 + 2 - 1)^4 \\
 &:= (-2 - 2 + 6 + 67 + 1 - 2 + 1)^4 \\
 &:= (2 + 2 - 6 + 67 + 1 + 2 + 1)^4 \\
 &:= (-2 + 26 + 67 - 1 - 21)^4 \\
 \mathbf{22714756} &:= (2 + 2 + 7 - 1 + 4756)^2 \\
 \mathbf{23149125} &:= (-231 + 491 + 25)^3 \\
 \mathbf{23393656} &:= (233 - 9 + 3 + 65 - 6)^3 \\
 &:= (23 - 393 + 656)^3 \\
 \mathbf{23639903} &:= (236 + 39 + 9 + 03)^3 \\
 &:= (2 + 363 + 9 - 90 + 3)^3 \\
 &:= (23 - 639 + 903)^3 \\
 \mathbf{23804641} &:= (238 + 04641)^2 \\
 \mathbf{24068836} &:= (2 + 4068 + 836)^2 \\
 \mathbf{24137569} &:= (2 + 4 - 1 + 3 + 7 + 5 + 6 - 9)^6 \\
 &:= (2 + 4 - 1 - 3 + 7 + 5 - 6 + 9)^6 \\
 &:= (2 - 4 + 1 + 3 + 7 + 5 - 6 + 9)^6 \\
 &:= (-2 + 4 + 1 - 3 + 7 - 5 + 6 + 9)^6 \\
 &:= (2 - 4 - 1 + 3 + 7 - 5 + 6 + 9)^6 \\
 &:= (2 + 4 + 1 - 3 - 7 + 5 + 6 + 9)^6 \\
 &:= (-2 + 4 - 1 + 3 - 7 + 5 + 6 + 9)^6 \\
 &:= (-2 - 4 - 1 - 3 + 7 + 5 + 6 + 9)^6 \\
 &:= (24 - 1 - 3 + 7 + 5 - 6 - 9)^6 \\
 &:= (24 + 1 - 3 - 7 + 5 + 6 - 9)^6 \\
 &:= (24 - 1 + 3 - 7 - 5 - 6 + 9)^6 \\
 &:= (-2 - 41 + 3 - 7 - 5 + 69)^6 \\
 &:= (2 + 4 + 1 - 37 + 56 - 9)^6 \\
 &:= (-24 - 13 + 7 + 56 - 9)^6 \\
 &:= (2 - 4 + 13 + 75 - 69)^6 \\
 &:= (24 - 13 + 75 - 69)^6 \\
 \mathbf{24492601} &:= (24 + 4926 - 01)^2 \\
 \mathbf{24502500} &:= (2450 + 2500)^2 \\
 \mathbf{24850225} &:= (-24 - 8 + 5022 - 5)^2
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 & := (2 - 5 + 1 + 5022 - 5)^2 \\
 \mathbf{25153757} & := (251 - 5 - 3 - 7 + 57)^3 \\
 \mathbf{25411681} & := (2 + 54 + 1 + 1 + 6 + 8 - 1)^4 \\
 & := (2 + 54 + 1 - 1 + 6 + 8 + 1)^4 \\
 & := (2 + 54 - 1 + 1 + 6 + 8 + 1)^4 \\
 & := (2 + 5 + 41 + 16 + 8 - 1)^4 \\
 & := (2 - 5 - 4 + 11 + 68 - 1)^4 \\
 & := (-2 + 5 + 4 - 11 - 6 + 81)^4 \\
 & := (-2 + 5 + 4 - 1 - 16 + 81)^4 \\
 & := (2 - 54 + 116 + 8 - 1)^4 \\
 \mathbf{25502500} & := (25 + 5025 + 00)^2 \\
 & := (2550 + 2500)^2 \\
 \mathbf{25934336} & := (259 + 3 + 43 - 3 - 6)^3 \\
 & := (259 - 3 + 43 + 3 - 6)^3 \\
 & := (-2 + 5 - 9 - 34 + 336)^3 \\
 \mathbf{26198073} & := (26 + 198 + 073)^3 \\
 \mathbf{26245129} & := (2 - 6 + 2 - 4 + 5129)^2 \\
 & := (-2 - 6 - 2 + 4 + 5129)^2 \\
 \mathbf{26463592} & := (264 + 6 + 35 - 9 + 2)^3 \\
 & := (264 - 63 + 5 + 92)^3 \\
 \mathbf{26512201} & := (26 + 5122 + 01)^2 \\
 \mathbf{26873856} & := (-2 + 6 - 8 + 73 - 8 + 5 + 6)^4 \\
 & := (2 + 6 + 8 + 7 + 38 + 5 + 6)^4 \\
 & := (2 - 6 + 8 + 7 - 3 + 8 + 56)^4 \\
 & := (-2 + 6 + 8 - 7 + 3 + 8 + 56)^4 \\
 & := (26 - 8 + 73 - 8 - 5 - 6)^4 \\
 & := (26 + 8 - 7 - 3 - 8 + 56)^4 \\
 & := (26 - 8 - 7 - 3 + 8 + 56)^4 \\
 & := (-2 + 68 - 73 + 85 - 6)^4 \\
 \mathbf{28005264} & := (28 + 005264)^2 \\
 \mathbf{28372625} & := (283 + 7 + 2 + 6 + 2 + 5)^3 \\
 & := (283 - 7 + 26 - 2 + 5)^3 \\
 & := (283 - 7 - 2 + 6 + 25)^3 \\
 & := (28 + 3 + 7 + 262 + 5)^3 \\
 & := (-2 - 8 + 372 - 62 + 5)^3 \\
 \mathbf{28398241} & := (-2 + 83 - 9 + 8 - 2 - 4 - 1)^4 \\
 & := (2 + 83 - 9 - 8 + 2 + 4 - 1)^4 \\
 & := (-2 - 8 - 3 + 9 + 82 - 4 - 1)^4 \\
 & := (2 - 8 + 3 - 9 + 82 + 4 - 1)^4 \\
 & := (-2 + 8 - 3 - 9 + 82 - 4 + 1)^4 \\
 & := (2 + 8 + 3 + 9 + 8 + 2 + 41)^4 \\
 & := (28 + 3 + 9 + 8 + 24 + 1)^4 \\
 & := (28 + 3 - 9 + 8 + 2 + 41)^4 \\
 & := (-2 + 83 + 9 + 8 - 24 - 1)^4 \\
 \mathbf{28629151} & := (2 + 8 - 6 + 2 + 9 + 15 + 1)^5 \\
 & := (2 - 8 - 6 + 2 - 9 - 1 + 51)^5 \\
 & := (28 + 6 + 2 + 9 - 15 + 1)^5 \\
 & := (28 - 6 + 2 - 9 + 15 + 1)^5 \\
 & := (2 + 86 + 2 - 9 + 1 - 51)^5 \\
 & := (-2 + 8 - 62 + 91 - 5 + 1)^5 \\
 & := (2 - 8 + 62 - 9 - 15 - 1)^5 \\
 & := (2 + 8 + 62 + 9 + 1 - 51)^5 \\
 & := (2 - 8 - 6 + 29 + 15 - 1)^5 \\
 & := (2 + 8 + 6 + 29 - 15 + 1)^5 \\
 & := (28 + 62 - 9 + 1 - 51)^5 \\
 \mathbf{28652616} & := (286 + 5 + 2 + 6 + 1 + 6)^3 \\
 & := (28 + 6 + 5 + 261 + 6)^3 \\
 \mathbf{28665316} & := (-28 + 66 + 5316)^2 \\
 \mathbf{28934443} & := (289 + 3 + 4 + 4 + 4 + 3)^3 \\
 \mathbf{29218112} & := (292 + 18 + 1 - 1 - 2)^3 \\
 & := (292 + 18 - 1 + 1 - 2)^3 \\
 & := (292 - 1 + 8 + 11 - 2)^3 \\
 \mathbf{29503629} & := (295 - 03 + 6 + 2 + 9)^3 \\
 \mathbf{29986576} & := (2 - 9 - 9 + 86 + 5 - 7 + 6)^4 \\
 & := (-2 - 9 - 9 + 86 - 5 + 7 + 6)^4 \\
 & := (-2 + 9 + 9 - 8 + 65 + 7 - 6)^4 \\
 & := (2 + 9 - 9 + 8 + 65 - 7 + 6)^4 \\
 & := (2 - 9 + 9 + 8 + 65 - 7 + 6)^4 \\
 & := (-29 + 9 + 86 - 5 + 7 + 6)^4 \\
 & := (-2 + 99 - 86 + 57 + 6)^4 \\
 \mathbf{30371328} & := (303 + 7 - 1 - 3 - 2 + 8)^3 \\
 \mathbf{30959144} & := (309 + 5 + 9 - 1 - 4 - 4)^3 \\
 & := (309 - 5 + 9 + 1 + 4 - 4)^3 \\
 & := (309 - 5 + 9 + 1 - 4 + 4)^3 \\
 & := (309 + 5 - 9 + 1 + 4 + 4)^3 \\
 \mathbf{31554496} & := (315 - 54 + 49 + 6)^3
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 \mathbf{31640625} &:= (3 - 1 + 64 + 06 - 2 + 5)^4 & &:= (33 - 5 + 5 - 4 + 4 - 3 + 2)^5 \\
 &:= (-3 + 1 + 64 + 06 + 2 + 5)^4 & &:= (-3 + 35 + 5 + 4 - 4 - 3 - 2)^5 \\
 &:= (-3 + 1 + 6 + 4 + 062 + 5)^4 & &:= (-3 + 35 + 5 - 4 + 4 - 3 - 2)^5 \\
 &:= (-3 + 1 + 6 + 40 + 6 + 25)^4 & &:= (3 + 35 - 5 + 4 - 4 - 3 + 2)^5 \\
 \mathbf{31685641} &:= (3 - 1 - 6 - 8 + 5641)^2 & &:= (3 + 35 - 5 - 4 + 4 - 3 + 2)^5 \\
 \mathbf{31956409} &:= (31 - 9 + 5640 - 9)^2 & &:= (-3 + 35 - 5 + 4 - 4 + 3 + 2)^5 \\
 &:= (3 + 19 + 5640 - 9)^2 & &:= (-3 + 35 - 5 - 4 + 4 + 3 + 2)^5 \\
 \mathbf{32157432} &:= (321 + 5 - 7 + 4 - 3 - 2)^3 & &:= (3 - 3 + 5 - 5 + 4 - 4 + 32)^5 \\
 &:= (321 - 5 + 7 - 4 - 3 + 2)^3 & &:= (-3 + 3 + 5 - 5 + 4 - 4 + 32)^5 \\
 &:= (321 - 5 - 7 + 4 + 3 + 2)^3 & &:= (3 - 3 - 5 + 5 + 4 - 4 + 32)^5 \\
 &:= (-3 + 215 + 74 + 32)^3 & &:= (-3 + 3 - 5 + 5 + 4 - 4 + 32)^5 \\
 \mathbf{32461759} &:= (324 + 61 - 75 + 9)^3 & &:= (3 - 3 + 5 - 5 - 4 + 4 + 32)^5 \\
 &:= (324 + 61 - 7 - 59)^3 & &:= (-3 + 3 + 5 - 5 - 4 + 4 + 32)^5 \\
 &:= (-3 + 246 + 17 + 59)^3 & &:= (3 - 3 - 5 + 5 - 4 + 4 + 32)^5 \\
 \mathbf{33076161} &:= (330 - 7 + 6 - 1 - 6 - 1)^3 & &:= (-3 + 3 - 5 + 5 - 4 + 4 + 32)^5 \\
 &:= (330 - 7 - 6 - 1 + 6 - 1)^3 & &:= (-33 - 5 - 5 + 44 + 3 - 2)^{25} \\
 &:= (3 + 307 - 6 + 16 + 1)^3 & &:= (33 + 5 + 5 + 4 - 43 - 2)^{25} \\
 \mathbf{33362176} &:= (3 + 3 + 3 - 6 - 2 - 1 + 76)^4 & &:= (-33 - 5 - 5 + 4 + 43 - 2)^{25} \\
 &:= (3 - 3 - 3 + 6 - 2 - 1 + 76)^4 & &:= (3 - 35 - 5 + 44 - 3 - 2)^{25} \\
 &:= (-3 + 3 - 3 + 6 - 2 - 1 + 76)^4 & &:= (-3 - 35 - 5 + 44 + 3 - 2)^{25} \\
 &:= (-3 - 3 + 3 + 6 - 2 - 1 + 76)^4 & &:= (3 + 35 + 5 + 4 - 43 - 2)^{25} \\
 &:= (3 + 3 - 3 - 6 + 2 + 1 + 76)^4 & &:= (-3 - 35 - 5 + 4 + 43 - 2)^{25} \\
 &:= (3 - 3 + 3 - 6 + 2 + 1 + 76)^4 & &:= (-3 - 3 - 5 + 54 - 43 + 2)^{25} \\
 &:= (-3 + 3 + 3 - 6 + 2 + 1 + 76)^4 & &:= (3 + 3 + 5 - 54 + 43 + 2)^{25} \\
 &:= (-3 - 3 - 3 + 6 + 2 + 1 + 76)^4 & &:= (3 - 3 - 5 - 5 + 44 - 32)^{25} \\
 &:= (33 + 3 + 6 + 21 + 7 + 6)^4 & &:= (-3 + 3 - 5 - 5 + 44 - 32)^{25} \\
 &:= (3 + 33 + 6 + 21 + 7 + 6)^4 & &:= (33 - 55 - 4 - 4 + 32)^{25} \\
 &:= (3 + 3 + 36 + 21 + 7 + 6)^4 & &:= (33 - 5 - 54 - 4 + 32)^{25} \\
 &:= (3 + 3 - 3 + 62 + 17 - 6)^4 & & \\
 &:= (3 - 3 + 3 + 62 + 17 - 6)^4 & & \\
 &:= (-3 + 3 + 3 + 62 + 17 - 6)^4 & & \\
 &:= (-3 - 3 - 3 + 62 + 17 + 6)^4 & & \\
 &:= (-33 + 36 - 2 - 1 + 76)^4 & & \\
 &:= (33 - 36 + 2 + 1 + 76)^4 & & \\
 \mathbf{33554432} &:= (33 - 5 - 5 + 4 + 4 + 3 - 2)^5 & & \\
 &:= (33 + 5 - 5 + 4 - 4 - 3 + 2)^5 & & \\
 &:= (33 - 5 + 5 + 4 - 4 - 3 + 2)^5 & & \\
 &:= (33 + 5 - 5 - 4 + 4 - 3 + 2)^5 & & \\
 \mathbf{33582025} &:= (3 - 3 + 5820 - 25)^2 & & \\
 &:= (-3 + 3 + 5820 - 25)^2 & & \\
 \mathbf{33698267} &:= (33 + 6 + 9 + 8 + 267)^3 & & \\
 &:= (3 + 36 + 9 + 8 + 267)^3 & & \\
 \mathbf{34012224} &:= (3 + 4 + 01 + 2 + 2 + 2 + 4)^6 & & \\
 &:= (-3 + 4 + 01 + 22 - 2 - 4)^6 & & \\
 &:= (3 - 4 - 01 + 22 + 2 - 4)^6 & & \\
 &:= (-3 - 4 + 01 + 22 - 2 + 4)^6 & & \\
 &:= (-3 + 4 + 01 - 2 + 22 - 4)^6 & & \\
 &:= (3 - 4 - 01 + 2 + 22 - 4)^6 & &
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 & := (-3 - 4 + 01 - 2 + 22 + 4)^6 \\
 & := (3 - 4 - 01 - 2 - 2 + 24)^6 \\
 & := (-3 - 4 + 01 + 2 - 2 + 24)^6 \\
 & := (-3 - 4 + 01 - 2 + 2 + 24)^6 \\
 & := (34 - 012 + 2 - 2 - 4)^6 \\
 & := (34 - 012 - 2 + 2 - 4)^6 \\
 & := (3 + 40 - 1 - 22 + 2 - 4)^6 \\
 & := (-3 + 40 + 1 - 22 - 2 + 4)^6 \\
 & := (3 + 40 - 1 + 2 - 22 - 4)^6 \\
 & := (-3 + 40 + 1 - 2 - 22 + 4)^6 \\
 & := (3 + 40 - 1 + 2 - 2 - 24)^6 \\
 & := (3 + 40 - 1 - 2 + 2 - 24)^6 \\
 & := (-3 + 40 + 1 + 2 + 2 - 24)^6 \\
 & := (340 - 12 + 2 - 2 - 4)^3 \\
 & := (340 - 12 - 2 + 2 - 4)^3 \\
 \mathbf{34328125} & := (343 - 2 - 8 - 1 - 2 - 5)^3 \\
 & := (-3 + 4 + 328 - 1 + 2 - 5)^3 \\
 & := (3 - 4 + 328 + 1 + 2 - 5)^3 \\
 & := (-3 - 4 + 328 + 1 - 2 + 5)^3 \\
 & := (343 - 2 + 8 + 1 - 25)^3 \\
 & := (34 + 3 + 281 + 2 + 5)^3 \\
 \mathbf{34645976} & := (-3 + 464 - 59 - 76)^3 \\
 \mathbf{35153041} & := (35 - 1 + 5 - 3 + 041)^4 \\
 & := (-3 + 5 - 1 + 5 + 30 + 41)^4 \\
 & := (35 + 15 + 30 - 4 + 1)^4 \\
 & := (-35 + 153 - 041)^4 \\
 \mathbf{35426304} & := (-354 + 2 + 6304)^2 \\
 \mathbf{35611289} & := (35 - 6 + 11 + 289)^3 \\
 \mathbf{35760400} & := (-3 - 57 + 6040 + 0)^2 \\
 \mathbf{35831808} & := (3 + 5 + 8 - 3 - 1 + 8 - 08)^7 \\
 & := (-3 + 5 + 8 + 3 - 1 + 8 - 08)^7 \\
 & := (3 + 5 + 8 - 3 - 1 - 8 + 08)^7 \\
 & := (-3 + 5 + 8 + 3 - 1 - 8 + 08)^7 \\
 & := (3 + 5 - 8 - 3 - 1 + 8 + 08)^7 \\
 & := (-3 - 5 + 8 - 3 - 1 + 8 + 08)^7 \\
 & := (-3 + 5 - 8 + 3 - 1 + 8 + 08)^7 \\
 & := (35 + 8 - 31 + 8 - 08)^7 \\
 & := (35 + 8 - 31 - 8 + 08)^7 \\
 & := (35 - 8 - 31 + 8 + 08)^7 \\
 & := (-3 + 5 + 83 - 1 - 80 + 8)^7 \\
 & := (3 + 5 - 83 - 1 + 80 + 8)^7 \\
 & := (35 - 831 + 808)^7 \\
 \mathbf{35916049} & := (35 - 91 + 6049)^2 \\
 \mathbf{35976004} & := (-3 - 5 + 9 - 7 + 6004)^2 \\
 \mathbf{36036009} & := (3 - 6 - 03 + 6009)^2 \\
 & := (-3 - 6 + 03 + 6009)^2 \\
 \mathbf{36264691} & := (3 - 6 + 264 + 69 + 1)^3 \\
 & := (-362 + 6 - 4 + 691)^3 \\
 \mathbf{36360900} & := (3 - 63 + 6090 + 0)^2 \\
 \mathbf{36594368} & := (365 - 9 + 4 - 36 + 8)^3 \\
 & := (-36 - 5 + 9 - 4 + 368)^3 \\
 & := (-36 + 5 - 9 + 4 + 368)^3 \\
 \mathbf{36857041} & := (368 + 5704 - 1)^2 \\
 \mathbf{36926037} & := (369 - 26 - 03 - 7)^3 \\
 \mathbf{37015056} & := (3 + 70 + 1 + 5 + 05 - 6)^4 \\
 & := (3 + 70 - 1 + 5 - 05 + 6)^4 \\
 & := (3 + 70 - 1 - 5 + 05 + 6)^4 \\
 & := (37 - 015 + 056)^4 \\
 & := (-3 - 70 + 150 - 5 + 6)^4 \\
 & := (3 + 70 - 1 - 50 + 56)^4 \\
 \mathbf{37613689} & := (3 - 7 + 6136 - 8 + 9)^2 \\
 \mathbf{37933056} & := (3 - 7 + 9 + 330 - 5 + 6)^3 \\
 & := (-3 + 7 - 9 + 330 + 5 + 6)^3 \\
 & := (37 - 9 - 3 + 305 + 6)^3 \\
 \mathbf{38272753} & := (-3 + 8 + 272 + 7 + 53)^3 \\
 & := (-382 + 727 - 5 - 3)^3 \\
 & := (38 + 27 + 275 - 3)^3 \\
 \mathbf{38614472} & := (386 + 1 - 44 - 7 + 2)^3 \\
 & := (386 + 1 - 4 - 47 + 2)^3 \\
 \mathbf{38950081} & := (3 + 8 + 9 + 50 + 08 + 1)^4 \\
 \mathbf{38958219} & := (389 - 58 - 2 + 1 + 9)^3 \\
 \mathbf{39135393} & := (39 + 1 + 3 + 5 - 3 - 9 - 3)^5 \\
 & := (39 + 1 - 3 + 5 + 3 - 9 - 3)^5 \\
 & := (39 - 1 - 3 - 5 - 3 + 9 - 3)^5 \\
 & := (39 + 1 - 3 + 5 - 3 - 9 + 3)^5 \\
 & := (39 - 1 + 3 - 5 + 3 - 9 + 3)^5
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 & := (3+9+13+5-3+9-3)^5 & := (4+3-04+6-7+2-1)^{16} \\
 & := (-3+9+13+5+3+9-3)^5 & := (-4+3+04+6-7+2-1)^{16} \\
 & := (-3+9+13+5-3+9+3)^5 & := (-4-3-04+6+7+2-1)^{16} \\
 & := (3+9+1+35-3-9-3)^5 & := (-4+3-04+6+7+2-1)^8 \\
 & := (-3+9+1+35+3-9-3)^5 & := (4-3+04+6-7-2+1)^{16} \\
 & := (3-9+1+35-3+9-3)^5 & := (4+3+04+6-7-2+1)^8 \\
 & := (-3-9+1+35+3+9-3)^5 & := (4+3-04-6+7-2+1)^{16} \\
 & := (-3+9+1+35-3-9+3)^5 & := (-4+3+04-6+7-2+1)^{16} \\
 & := (-3-9+1+35-3+9+3)^5 & := (4-3-04+6+7-2+1)^8 \\
 & := (3-9+1-3+53-9-3)^5 & := (-4-3+04+6+7-2+1)^8 \\
 & := (-3-9+1+3+53-9-3)^5 & := (4-3+04-6+7+2+1)^8 \\
 & := (-3-9+1-3+53-9+3)^5 & := (4+3+04+67+2+1)^4 \\
 & := (-3+9-1-3-5+39-3)^5 & := (4+3+04+6+7-21)^{16} \\
 & := (3-9+1-3+5+39-3)^5 & := (-4+3-04-6-7+21)^{16} \\
 & := (-3-9+1+3+5+39-3)^5 & := (-4-3-04+6-7+21)^8 \\
 & := (3-9-1+3-5+39+3)^5 & := (43+046-7-2+1)^4 \\
 & := (-3-9+1-3+5+39+3)^5 & := (43-046+7-2+1)^{16} \\
 & := (-39+13+53+9-3)^5 & := (-43+046+7-2+1)^8 \\
 & := (-39-13-5-3+93)^5 & := (43+04+6+7+21)^4 \\
 & := (39+1+35-39-3)^5 & := (4+3+046+7+21)^4 \\
 & := (-39+1+35+39-3)^5 & := (4+30+46-72+1)^8 \\
 & := (3+91+35-3-93)^5 & \mathbf{43243551} := (-4+3+2-4+355-1)^3 \\
 & := (-3+91+35+3-93)^5 & := (4-3-2-4+355+1)^3 \\
 & := (3-9+135-3-93)^5 & := (-4-3-2+4+355+1)^3 \\
 & := (-3-9+135+3-93)^5 & := (-4+324+35-5+1)^3 \\
 & := (-3+9-13-53+93)^5 & := (43-243+551)^3 \\
 & := (391+35-393)^5 & \mathbf{43614208} := (4-3-61+420-8)^3 \\
 \mathbf{40353607} & := (40-35+3+6-07)^9 & \mathbf{43986977} := (-439+869-77)^3 \\
 & := (4+03-53+60-7)^9 & \mathbf{43996689} := (43-99+6689)^2 \\
 & := (4+03+53-60+7)^9 & \mathbf{44361864} := (443-6-1-86+4)^3 \\
 & := (-4-03-53+60+7)^9 & \mathbf{45118016} := (451+1-80-16)^3 \\
 \mathbf{40707584} & := (407-075+8+4)^3 & \mathbf{45212176} := (45+21+2+1+7+6)^4 \\
 \mathbf{41063625} & := (4-10-6+362-5)^3 & := (45+2+1+21+7+6)^4 \\
 \mathbf{41216400} & := (41-21+6400)^2 & := (4+52+12+1+7+6)^4 \\
 \mathbf{41421736} & := (414-2+1-73+6)^3 & := (4+52+1+2+17+6)^4 \\
 \mathbf{42144192} & := (-4+2+1+441-92)^3 & := (-4-5+2+12+1+76)^4 \\
 \mathbf{43046721} & := (4-3+04-6+7-2-1)^{16} & := (45+2+12+17+6)^4 \\
 & := (4+3+04-6+7-2-1)^8 & \mathbf{45435424} := (4+5-4+35-4+2-4)^5
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 & := (-4 + 5 + 4 + 35 - 4 + 2 - 4)^5 \\
 & := (-4 + 5 - 4 + 35 + 4 + 2 - 4)^5 \\
 & := (-4 + 5 - 4 + 35 - 4 + 2 + 4)^5 \\
 & := (45 + 4 - 35 - 4 + 24)^5 \\
 & := (45 - 4 - 35 + 4 + 24)^5 \\
 & := (-45 + 4 - 3 + 54 + 24)^5 \\
 & := (4 - 5 - 43 + 54 + 24)^5 \\
 & := (45 - 435 + 424)^5 \\
 \mathbf{45882712} & := (-4 + 5 + 88 + 271 - 2)^3 \\
 \mathbf{46063369} & := (460 + 6336 - 9)^2 \\
 \mathbf{46268279} & := (4 + 62 + 6 + 8 + 279)^3 \\
 & := (4 + 6 + 268 + 2 + 79)^3 \\
 & := (4 + 6 + 2 + 68 + 279)^3 \\
 & := (46 + 26 + 8 + 279)^3 \\
 & := (4 + 626 + 8 - 279)^3 \\
 \mathbf{46676224} & := (46 + 6762 + 24)^2 \\
 \mathbf{46840336} & := (4 + 6840 + 3 + 3 - 6)^2 \\
 \mathbf{46840336} & := (4 + 6840 - 3 - 3 + 6)^2 \\
 \mathbf{46977316} & := (-469 + 7 + 7316)^2 \\
 \mathbf{47045881} & := (4 + 7 + 04 + 5 + 8 - 8 - 1)^6 \\
 & := (4 + 7 + 04 + 5 - 8 + 8 - 1)^6 \\
 & := (-4 + 7 - 04 + 5 + 8 + 8 - 1)^6 \\
 & := (4 + 7 - 04 - 5 + 8 + 8 + 1)^6 \\
 & := (-4 + 7 + 04 - 5 + 8 + 8 + 1)^6 \\
 & := (-4 - 7 + 045 - 8 - 8 + 1)^6 \\
 & := (47 - 045 + 8 + 8 + 1)^6 \\
 & := (4 + 70 - 4 - 58 + 8 - 1)^6 \\
 & := (-4 + 70 + 4 - 58 + 8 - 1)^6 \\
 & := (47 + 045 + 8 - 81)^6 \\
 & := (470 - 458 + 8 - 1)^6 \\
 \mathbf{47073321} & := (-470 + 7332 - 1)^2 \\
 \mathbf{47196900} & := (-4 - 7 - 19 + 6900)^2 \\
 \mathbf{47306884} & := (4 - 7 - 3 + 06884)^2 \\
 \mathbf{47437928} & := (4 - 7 - 4 + 379 - 2 - 8)^3 \\
 & := (-4 - 7 + 4 + 379 - 2 - 8)^3 \\
 \mathbf{47458321} & := (-4 + 74 + 5 + 8 + 3 - 2 - 1)^4 \\
 & := (4 + 74 - 5 + 8 + 3 - 2 + 1)^4 \\
 & := (-4 + 74 + 5 + 8 - 3 + 2 + 1)^4 \\
 & := (4 + 74 - 5 - 8 - 3 + 21)^4 \\
 & := (4 + 7 - 4 + 58 - 3 + 21)^4 \\
 & := (-4 + 7 + 4 + 58 - 3 + 21)^4 \\
 & := (4 - 7 + 4 + 58 + 3 + 21)^4 \\
 & := (47 - 4 + 58 + 3 - 21)^4 \\
 \mathbf{47832147} & := (47 - 8 + 321 - 4 + 7)^3 \\
 & := (-4 + 7 - 8 + 321 + 47)^3 \\
 & := (478 + 32 - 147)^3 \\
 \mathbf{48228544} & := (48 - 228 + 544)^3 \\
 \mathbf{48566961} & := (-48 + 56 + 6961)^2 \\
 \mathbf{48828125} & := (-4 + 8 + 8 + 2 + 8 - 12 - 5)^{11} \\
 & := (4 + 8 - 8 + 2 - 8 + 12 - 5)^{11} \\
 & := (4 - 8 + 8 + 2 - 8 + 12 - 5)^{11} \\
 & := (4 - 8 - 8 + 2 + 8 + 12 - 5)^{11} \\
 & := (48 - 8 - 28 - 12 + 5)^{11} \\
 & := (-48 + 8 + 28 + 12 + 5)^{11} \\
 & := (-4 - 88 - 28 + 125)^{11} \\
 \mathbf{49787136} & := (-4 + 97 + 8 - 7 - 1 - 3 - 6)^4 \\
 & := (-4 + 97 - 8 + 7 + 1 - 3 - 6)^4 \\
 & := (4 + 97 - 8 - 7 + 1 + 3 - 6)^4 \\
 & := (4 - 9 + 78 + 7 + 1 - 3 + 6)^4 \\
 & := (-4 + 9 + 78 - 7 - 1 + 3 + 6)^4 \\
 & := (4 - 9 + 7 + 8 + 71 - 3 + 6)^4 \\
 & := (-4 + 9 + 7 - 8 + 71 + 3 + 6)^4 \\
 \mathbf{49836032} & := (-4 + 9 + 8 + 360 - 3 - 2)^3 \\
 & := (4 - 9 + 8 + 360 + 3 + 2)^3 \\
 \mathbf{50243409} & := (5 - 02 - 43 + 409)^3 \\
 \mathbf{50653000} & := (5 + 065 + 300 + 0)^3 \\
 \mathbf{51064811} & := (-5 - 106 + 481 + 1)^3 \\
 \mathbf{51710481} & := (5 + 1 + 7104 + 81)^2 \\
 \mathbf{52200625} & := (52 + 20 + 06 + 2 + 5)^4 \\
 & := (52 + 2 + 006 + 25)^4 \\
 \mathbf{52313624} & := (5 - 2 + 313 + 62 - 4)^3 \\
 \mathbf{52521875} & := (5 + 2 + 5 + 2 + 1 + 8 + 7 + 5)^5 \\
 & := (5 + 25 - 2 + 1 + 8 - 7 + 5)^5 \\
 & := (5 + 25 + 2 - 1 - 8 + 7 + 5)^5 \\
 & := (5 - 2 + 5 + 21 + 8 - 7 + 5)^5
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 & := (52 + 5 - 2 - 18 - 7 + 5)^5 & := (5 - 9 + 9 + 69 + 5 + 3 + 6)^4 \\
 & := (-52 + 5 - 2 + 1 + 8 + 75)^5 & := (59 - 9 + 6 - 9 + 5 + 36)^4 \\
 & := (-5 + 25 + 21 - 8 + 7 - 5)^5 & := (5 + 99 + 6 + 9 + 5 - 36)^4 \\
 & := (5 - 2 + 52 - 18 - 7 + 5)^5 & := (5 + 9 + 96 + 9 + 5 - 36)^4 \\
 & := (5 - 2 - 52 + 1 + 8 + 75)^5 & := (5 + 9 + 9 + 6 + 95 - 36)^4 \\
 & := (5 - 25 - 2 - 18 + 75)^5 & := (59 - 9 + 69 + 5 - 36)^4 \\
 \mathbf{52867441} & := (528 + 6744 - 1)^2 & \mathbf{60236288} & := (-60 + 2 + 362 + 88)^3 \\
 \mathbf{52881984} & := (5288 + 1984)^2 & \mathbf{60466176} & := (6 + 04 + 6 + 6 + 1 + 7 + 6)^5 \\
 \mathbf{53157376} & := (-5 + 315 - 7 - 3 + 76)^3 & & := (-6 + 046 - 6 + 1 + 7 - 6)^5 \\
 & := (-5 - 3 + 15 - 7 + 376)^3 & & := (60 - 46 + 6 - 1 - 7 - 6)^{10} \\
 & := (5 + 3 - 15 + 7 + 376)^3 & & := (60 - 46 - 6 - 1 - 7 + 6)^{10} \\
 \mathbf{53582633} & := (5 + 358 + 2 + 6 + 3 + 3)^3 & & := (-60 + 46 + 6 + 1 + 7 + 6)^{10} \\
 & := (53 + 58 + 263 + 3)^3 & \mathbf{60481729} & := (6048 + 1729)^2 \\
 \mathbf{54010152} & := (540 - 10 - 152)^3 & \mathbf{61629875} & := (6 + 16 + 298 + 75)^3 \\
 \mathbf{54597321} & := (54 + 5 + 9 + 7321)^2 & \mathbf{62078641} & := (-6 + 20 + 7864 + 1)^2 \\
 & := (5 + 4 + 59 + 7321)^2 & \mathbf{62267881} & := (-6 + 22 - 6 + 7881)^2 \\
 \mathbf{54700816} & := (5 - 4 + 70 + 08 + 1 + 6)^4 & \mathbf{62678889} & := (-6 + 26 + 7888 + 9)^2 \\
 \mathbf{54745201} & := (-54 + 7452 + 01)^2 & \mathbf{62742241} & := (6 + 2 + 74 + 2 + 2 + 4 - 1)^4 \\
 \mathbf{56175025} & := (5 - 6 - 1 + 7502 - 5)^2 & & := (-6 + 2 + 74 + 22 - 4 + 1)^4 \\
 & := (-5 - 6 - 1 + 7502 + 5)^2 & & := (-6 - 2 + 74 - 2 + 24 + 1)^4 \\
 \mathbf{56746089} & := (56 + 7460 + 8 + 9)^2 & & := (-6 + 2 + 74 - 22 + 41)^4 \\
 \mathbf{56896849} & := (5 + 689 + 6849)^2 & & := (-62 - 74 + 224 + 1)^4 \\
 \mathbf{57289761} & := (-5 + 7 - 2 + 89 - 7 + 6 - 1)^4 & \mathbf{62748517} & := (6 - 2 - 7 - 4 + 8 - 5 + 17)^7 \\
 & := (5 - 7 + 2 + 89 - 7 + 6 - 1)^4 & & := (-6 + 2 - 7 + 4 + 8 - 5 + 17)^7 \\
 & := (-5 - 7 - 2 + 89 + 7 + 6 - 1)^4 & & := (-6 + 2 + 7 - 4 - 8 + 5 + 17)^7 \\
 & := (5 + 7 - 2 + 89 - 7 - 6 + 1)^4 & & := (62 + 7 - 4 - 8 - 51 + 7)^7 \\
 & := (5 - 7 - 2 + 89 + 7 - 6 + 1)^4 & & := (-6 - 27 - 4 - 8 + 51 + 7)^7 \\
 & := (57 + 2 - 8 + 97 - 61)^4 & & := (-6 + 27 - 4 + 8 + 5 - 17)^7 \\
 & := (-5 - 72 + 89 + 76 - 1)^4 & & := (6 - 27 + 4 + 8 + 5 + 17)^7 \\
 \mathbf{57562569} & := (5 + 7562 + 5 + 6 + 9)^2 & & := (6 + 2 - 74 + 85 + 1 - 7)^7 \\
 \mathbf{57592921} & := (5 + 7592 - 9 + 2 - 1)^2 & & := (-6 + 2 - 74 + 85 - 1 + 7)^7 \\
 \mathbf{57623281} & := (-5 + 7623 - 28 + 1)^2 & & := (-6 + 2 + 7 - 48 + 51 + 7)^7 \\
 \mathbf{57653649} & := (-5 + 7653 - 64 + 9)^2 & \mathbf{63297936} & := (6 + 3 + 2 + 9 + 7936)^2 \\
 \mathbf{57653649} & := (-5 + 7653 - 6 - 49)^2 & & := (-6 - 3 + 29 + 7936)^2 \\
 \mathbf{57775201} & := (5 + 77 + 7520 - 1)^2 & \mathbf{63792169} & := (63 + 7921 - 6 + 9)^2 \\
 \mathbf{57927321} & := (5 + 7927 - 321)^2 & & := (-6 + 3 + 7921 + 69)^2 \\
 \mathbf{59969536} & := (5 + 9 + 9 + 69 + 5 - 3 - 6)^4 & \mathbf{63968004} & := (6 + 3 - 9 - 6 + 8004)^2 \\
 & := (5 + 9 - 9 + 69 + 5 + 3 + 6)^4 & & := (-6 - 3 + 9 - 6 + 8004)^2
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 & := (-6 + 3 - 9 + 6 + 8004)^2 \\
 \mathbf{64048009} & := (-6 + 4 - 04 + 8009)^2 \\
 & := (-6 - 4 + 04 + 8009)^2 \\
 \mathbf{64080025} & := (-6 + 4 + 08002 + 5)^2 \\
 \mathbf{64480900} & := (-64 + 4 + 8090 + 0)^2 \\
 \mathbf{64964808} & := (6 + 4 - 96 + 480 + 8)^3 \\
 \mathbf{65939264} & := (6 - 5 + 9 + 392 + 6 - 4)^3 \\
 & := (6 + 5 - 9 + 392 + 6 + 4)^3 \\
 \mathbf{66080641} & := (66 + 08064 - 1)^2 \\
 & := (6 + 60 + 8064 - 1)^2 \\
 \mathbf{66923416} & := (6 - 6 - 9 + 2 - 3 + 416)^3 \\
 & := (-6 + 6 - 9 + 2 - 3 + 416)^3 \\
 & := (66 - 9 + 2 + 341 + 6)^3 \\
 \mathbf{67108864} & := (6 + 7 - 1 + 08 - 8 - 6 - 4)^{26} \\
 & := (6 + 7 + 1 + 08 - 8 - 6 - 4)^{13} \\
 & := (6 + 7 - 1 - 08 + 8 - 6 - 4)^{26} \\
 & := (6 + 7 + 1 - 08 + 8 - 6 - 4)^{13} \\
 & := (6 - 7 - 1 + 08 + 8 - 6 - 4)^{13} \\
 & := (-6 + 7 - 1 + 08 - 8 + 6 - 4)^{26} \\
 & := (6 - 7 + 1 + 08 - 8 + 6 - 4)^{26} \\
 & := (-6 + 7 + 1 + 08 - 8 + 6 - 4)^{13} \\
 & := (-6 + 7 - 1 - 08 + 8 + 6 - 4)^{26} \\
 & := (6 - 7 + 1 - 08 + 8 + 6 - 4)^{26} \\
 & := (-6 + 7 + 1 - 08 + 8 + 6 - 4)^{13} \\
 & := (-6 - 7 - 1 + 08 + 8 + 6 - 4)^{13} \\
 & := (-6 - 7 + 1 + 08 + 8 - 6 + 4)^{26} \\
 & := (67 - 1 + 08 - 8 - 64)^{26} \\
 & := (67 + 1 + 08 - 8 - 64)^{13} \\
 & := (67 - 1 - 08 + 8 - 64)^{26} \\
 & := (67 + 1 - 08 + 8 - 64)^{13} \\
 \mathbf{67419143} & := (6 - 7 + 419 - 14 + 3)^3 \\
 \mathbf{67848169} & := (-6 + 78 - 4 + 8169)^2 \\
 \mathbf{68244121} & := (6 + 8244 + 12 - 1)^2 \\
 \mathbf{68574961} & := (6 + 8 + 57 + 4 + 9 + 6 + 1)^4 \\
 & := (6 - 8 + 5 + 74 + 9 + 6 - 1)^4 \\
 & := (6 + 8 + 5 + 74 - 9 + 6 + 1)^4 \\
 & := (-6 + 8 + 5 - 7 - 4 + 96 - 1)^4 \\
 & := (6 - 8 - 5 + 7 - 4 + 96 - 1)^4 \\
 & := (-6 - 8 + 5 + 7 - 4 + 96 + 1)^4 \\
 & := (-6 + 8 - 5 - 7 + 4 + 96 + 1)^4 \\
 & := (-6 - 8 + 57 - 4 - 9 + 61)^4 \\
 \mathbf{69343957} & := (-6 + 9 + 34 + 3 + 9 - 5 - 7)^5 \\
 & := (-6 + 9 + 34 - 3 - 9 + 5 + 7)^5 \\
 & := (6 - 9 + 34 + 3 - 9 + 5 + 7)^5 \\
 & := (-6 - 9 + 34 - 3 + 9 + 5 + 7)^5 \\
 & := (-6 + 9 + 3 + 4 + 39 - 5 - 7)^5 \\
 & := (-6 + 9 - 3 - 4 + 39 - 5 + 7)^5 \\
 & := (6 - 9 + 3 - 4 + 39 - 5 + 7)^5 \\
 & := (-6 - 9 - 3 + 4 + 39 + 5 + 7)^5 \\
 & := (-6 - 9 + 3 + 4 - 3 - 9 + 57)^5 \\
 & := (-6 - 9 - 3 + 4 + 3 - 9 + 57)^5 \\
 & := (-69 + 3 + 4 - 3 + 95 + 7)^5 \\
 & := (-69 - 3 + 4 + 3 + 95 + 7)^5 \\
 & := (-6 + 93 - 43 - 9 - 5 + 7)^5 \\
 & := (-69 - 3 + 43 + 9 + 57)^5 \\
 & := (-6 - 9 + 34 - 39 + 57)^5 \\
 \mathbf{69426531} & := (-69 + 426 + 53 + 1)^3 \\
 & := (6 + 942 - 6 - 531)^3 \\
 & := (-6 + 942 + 6 - 531)^3 \\
 & := (6942 - 6531)^3 \\
 \mathbf{70829056} & := (70 + 8290 + 56)^2 \\
 \mathbf{71284249} & := (7 + 1 + 2 + 8424 + 9)^2 \\
 \mathbf{71639296} & := (7 - 1 + 6 + 3 + 92 - 9 - 6)^4 \\
 & := (7 - 1 - 6 - 3 + 92 + 9 - 6)^4 \\
 & := (-7 + 1 + 6 - 3 + 92 + 9 - 6)^4 \\
 & := (7 - 1 - 6 + 3 + 92 - 9 + 6)^4 \\
 & := (-7 + 1 + 6 + 3 + 92 - 9 + 6)^4 \\
 & := (-7 + 1 - 6 - 3 + 92 + 9 + 6)^4 \\
 & := (-7 - 1 - 6 + 3 + 9 - 2 + 96)^4 \\
 & := (7 - 1 - 6 + 3 - 9 + 2 + 96)^4 \\
 & := (-7 + 1 + 6 + 3 - 9 + 2 + 96)^4 \\
 & := (-7 + 1 - 6 - 3 + 9 + 2 + 96)^4 \\
 \mathbf{73034632} & := (73 + 0346 - 3 + 2)^3 \\
 \mathbf{73085401} & := (7 + 3 + 08540 - 1)^2 \\
 \mathbf{73856836} & := (-7 - 3 + 8568 + 36)^2 \\
 \mathbf{74805201} & := (7 + 4 + 80 + 5 - 2 - 01)^4
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 &:= (-7 - 4 + 80 + 5 + 20 - 1)^4 \\
 &:= (-7 + 4 + 80 - 5 + 20 + 1)^4 \\
 \mathbf{75151448} &:= (-7 - 5 - 15 + 1 + 448)^3 \\
 &:= (7 - 51 + 514 - 48)^3 \\
 \mathbf{75968656} &:= (75 - 9 - 6 + 8656)^2 \\
 &:= (7 + 59 - 6 + 8656)^2 \\
 \mathbf{76860289} &:= (76 + 8602 + 89)^2 \\
 \mathbf{76895361} &:= (-768 + 9536 + 1)^2 \\
 \mathbf{78074896} &:= (78 + 07 + 4 + 8 - 9 + 6)^4 \\
 &:= (7 + 8 + 074 + 8 - 9 + 6)^4 \\
 &:= (-7 + 8 - 07 - 4 + 8 + 96)^4 \\
 &:= (-7 + 80 - 74 + 89 + 6)^4 \\
 \mathbf{78402752} &:= (78 - 402 + 752)^3 \\
 \mathbf{78428736} &:= (78 + 42 + 8736)^2 \\
 \mathbf{78818884} &:= (-7 + 8 - 8 + 1 + 8884)^2 \\
 &:= (-7 - 8 + 8 + 1 + 8884)^2 \\
 \mathbf{78889924} &:= (-7 - 8 + 8899 + 2 - 4)^2 \\
 \mathbf{78953589} &:= (-7 - 8 + 95 + 358 - 9)^3 \\
 \mathbf{79049881} &:= (7904 + 988 - 1)^2 \\
 \mathbf{79235168} &:= (7 + 9 + 2 + 35 - 1 - 6 - 8)^5 \\
 &:= (-7 + 9 + 2 + 35 + 1 + 6 - 8)^5 \\
 &:= (-7 + 9 - 2 + 35 + 1 - 6 + 8)^5 \\
 &:= (7 - 9 + 2 + 35 + 1 - 6 + 8)^5 \\
 &:= (-7 + 9 + 2 - 3 + 51 - 6 - 8)^5 \\
 &:= (-7 - 9 + 2 + 3 + 51 + 6 - 8)^5 \\
 &:= (-7 - 9 - 2 + 3 + 51 - 6 + 8)^5 \\
 &:= (79 - 23 - 5 + 1 - 6 - 8)^5 \\
 &:= (7 + 92 + 3 + 5 - 1 - 68)^5 \\
 &:= (-7 + 9 + 23 + 5 + 16 - 8)^5 \\
 &:= (-7 + 9 + 2 - 35 + 1 + 68)^5 \\
 &:= (7 + 9 + 2 + 3 - 51 + 68)^5 \\
 &:= (79 + 23 + 5 - 1 - 68)^5 \\
 &:= (79 + 2 - 35 - 16 + 8)^5 \\
 &:= (7 - 9 + 23 - 51 + 68)^5 \\
 \mathbf{79388100} &:= (7 + 93 + 8810 + 0)^2 \\
 \mathbf{79887844} &:= (7 + 9 + 8878 + 44)^2 \\
 \mathbf{80910025} &:= (-80 + 9100 - 25)^2 \\
 \mathbf{81090025} &:= (8 - 10 + 9002 + 5)^2
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 \mathbf{81450625} &:= (81 - 4 + 5 + 06 + 2 + 5)^4 \\
 &:= (-8 + 1 + 45 + 062 - 5)^4 \\
 &:= (81 + 45 - 06 - 25)^4 \\
 &:= (-8 - 14 + 50 + 62 + 5)^4 \\
 \mathbf{82828201} &:= (8282 + 820 - 1)^2 \\
 \mathbf{84787264} &:= (8478 + 726 + 4)^2 \\
 \mathbf{84934656} &:= (8 + 4 + 93 - 4 + 6 - 5 - 6)^4 \\
 &:= (8 - 4 + 93 + 4 + 6 - 5 - 6)^4 \\
 &:= (8 + 4 + 93 - 4 - 6 - 5 + 6)^4 \\
 &:= (8 - 4 + 93 + 4 - 6 - 5 + 6)^4 \\
 &:= (8 + 49 + 34 + 6 + 5 - 6)^4 \\
 &:= (8 + 49 + 34 - 6 + 5 + 6)^4 \\
 &:= (-8 + 49 - 3 - 4 + 6 + 56)^4 \\
 &:= (8 + 4 - 9 + 34 + 65 - 6)^4 \\
 &:= (-8 - 4 + 9 - 3 + 46 + 56)^4 \\
 \mathbf{85766121} &:= (8 - 5 + 7 + 6 - 6 + 12 - 1)^6 \\
 &:= (8 - 5 + 7 - 6 + 6 + 12 - 1)^6 \\
 &:= (8 + 5 + 7 + 6 + 6 - 12 + 1)^6 \\
 &:= (8 + 5 + 7 - 6 - 6 + 12 + 1)^6 \\
 &:= (8 - 5 - 7 + 6 + 6 + 12 + 1)^6 \\
 &:= (8 - 57 + 66 + 1 + 2 + 1)^6 \\
 &:= (8 - 57 + 6 + 61 + 2 + 1)^6 \\
 &:= (8 - 5 + 76 - 61 + 2 + 1)^6 \\
 &:= (-8 - 57 + 66 - 1 + 21)^6 \\
 &:= (8 + 57 - 66 + 1 + 21)^6 \\
 &:= (-8 + 576 - 6 - 121)^3 \\
 \mathbf{86192656} &:= (8 + 6 - 1 + 9265 + 6)^2 \\
 \mathbf{86769225} &:= (8 + 6 + 76 + 9225)^2 \\
 &:= (8695 + 5 + 625)^2 \\
 \mathbf{88529281} &:= (88 + 5 + 2 + 9 + 2 - 8 - 1)^4 \\
 &:= (88 - 5 - 2 + 9 - 2 + 8 + 1)^4 \\
 &:= (88 + 5 + 2 - 9 + 2 + 8 + 1)^4 \\
 &:= (8 + 85 + 2 + 9 + 2 - 8 - 1)^4 \\
 &:= (-8 + 85 + 2 + 9 + 2 + 8 - 1)^4 \\
 &:= (8 + 85 + 2 - 9 + 2 + 8 + 1)^4 \\
 &:= (8 + 8 - 5 - 2 + 9 - 2 + 81)^4 \\
 &:= (8 + 8 + 5 + 2 - 9 + 2 + 81)^4 \\
 &:= (-8 + 85 + 29 - 2 - 8 + 1)^4
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 & := (-8 + 85 + 2 - 9 + 28 - 1)^4 \\
 & := (-8 - 8 + 5 + 29 - 2 + 81)^4 \\
 \mathbf{88716536} & := (-88 - 7 - 1 + 6 + 536)^3 \\
 & := (-8 - 87 - 1 + 6 + 536)^3 \\
 \mathbf{89453764} & := (8 + 9453 + 7 - 6 - 4)^2 \\
 \mathbf{90518849} & := (-90 + 518 + 8 + 4 + 9)^3 \\
 \mathbf{90649441} & := (90 - 6 - 4 + 9441)^2 \\
 \mathbf{90954369} & := (9 + 09543 - 6 - 9)^2 \\
 & := (-9 + 09543 - 6 + 9)^2 \\
 \mathbf{90973444} & := (9097 - 3 + 444)^2 \\
 \mathbf{91733851} & := (-9 + 1 + 73 + 385 + 1)^3 \\
 \mathbf{91795561} & := (9 + 17 + 9556 - 1)^2 \\
 \mathbf{91891396} & := (9189 + 1 + 396)^2 \\
 \mathbf{91968100} & := (-91 + 9681 + 00)^2 \\
 \mathbf{92236816} & := (92 + 2 - 3 + 6 + 8 - 1 - 6)^4 \\
 & := (92 + 2 - 3 - 6 + 8 - 1 + 6)^4 \\
 & := (92 - 2 + 3 + 6 - 8 + 1 + 6)^4 \\
 & := (-9 - 2 - 2 + 36 + 81 - 6)^4 \\
 & := (9 - 22 + 36 + 81 - 6)^4 \\
 \mathbf{92345408} & := (-9 + 2 - 3 + 454 + 08)^3 \\
 & := (92 - 3 - 45 + 408)^3 \\
 \mathbf{92563641} & := (9256 + 364 + 1)^2 \\
 \mathbf{92929600} & := (9 + 29 + 2 + 9600)^2 \\
 \mathbf{93973636} & := (-9 + 3 + 9736 - 36)^2 \\
 \mathbf{94196375} & := (94 + 1 - 9 - 6 + 375)^3 \\
 \mathbf{94818816} & := (-9 + 481 + 8 - 8 - 16)^3 \\
 & := (-9 + 481 - 8 + 8 - 16)^3 \\
 \mathbf{94984516} & := (-94 + 9845 + 1 - 6)^2
 \end{aligned}$$

7.8 9-Digits Semi-Selfie Numbers

$$\begin{aligned}
 \mathbf{10000000} & := (10 + 0000000)^8 \\
 & := (100 + 000000)^4 \\
 & := (10000 + 0000)^2 \\
 \mathbf{100020001} & := (10002 + 000 - 1)^2 \\
 \mathbf{100180081} & := (10018 - 008 - 1)^2 \\
 \mathbf{100200100} & := (10020 - 010 + 0)^2 \\
 \mathbf{100220121} & := (10022 - 012 + 1)^2 \\
 \mathbf{100280196} & := (10028 + 01 - 9 - 6)^2 \\
 \mathbf{100544625} & := (-1 + 005 + 4 + 462 - 5)^3 \\
 & := (-1 - 005 + 4 + 462 + 5)^3 \\
 & := (-1 - 005 + 446 + 25)^3 \\
 \mathbf{100721296} & := (10072 - 1 - 29 - 6)^2 \\
 \mathbf{100881936} & := (10088 + 1 - 9 - 36)^2 \\
 \mathbf{100902025} & := (10090 - 20 - 25)^2
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 \mathbf{111049444} &:= (1 - 1 + 10494 + 44)^2 & &:= (-11 - 33 + 79 - 9 - 04)^6 \\
 &:= (-1 + 1 + 10494 + 44)^2 & &:= (-1 + 133 - 7 - 99 - 04)^6 \\
 \mathbf{111284641} &:= (11 + 1 - 2 + 8 + 464 - 1)^3 & &:= (-1 + 133 - 7 - 9 - 90 - 4)^6 \\
 &:= (11 - 1 - 2 + 8 + 464 + 1)^3 & &:= (-1 + 13 + 3 - 79 + 90 - 4)^6 \\
 &:= (1 + 11 - 2 + 8 + 464 - 1)^3 & & \\
 &:= (-1 + 11 - 2 + 8 + 464 + 1)^3 & & \\
 &:= (-1 - 1 + 12 + 8 + 464 - 1)^3 & & \\
 &:= (-11 + 1 + 28 + 464 - 1)^3 & & \\
 &:= (-11 - 1 + 28 + 464 + 1)^3 & & \\
 &:= (1 - 11 + 28 + 464 - 1)^3 & & \\
 &:= (-1 - 11 + 28 + 464 + 1)^3 & & \\
 \mathbf{111746041} &:= (11174 - 604 + 1)^2 & & \\
 \mathbf{112550881} &:= (1 + 1 + 2 + 5 + 5 + 088 + 1)^4 & & \\
 &:= (1 + 1 + 2 + 5 + 5 + 08 + 81)^4 & & \\
 &:= (112 - 5 - 5 + 08 - 8 + 1)^4 & & \\
 &:= (112 - 5 - 5 - 08 + 8 + 1)^4 & & \\
 &:= (1 - 1 + 25 + 5 - 08 + 81)^4 & & \\
 &:= (-1 + 1 + 25 + 5 - 08 + 81)^4 & & \\
 &:= (11 + 25 + 50 + 8 + 8 + 1)^4 & & \\
 &:= (-11 - 25 + 50 + 88 + 1)^4 & & \\
 &:= (-11 - 25 + 50 + 8 + 81)^4 & & \\
 &:= (1 + 125 + 50 + 8 - 81)^4 & & \\
 \mathbf{112678587} &:= (1 - 1 - 26 - 78 + 587)^3 & & \\
 &:= (-1 + 1 - 26 - 78 + 587)^3 & & \\
 \mathbf{113379904} &:= (11 + 3 - 3 + 7 + 9 - 9 + 04)^6 & & \\
 &:= (11 - 3 + 3 + 7 + 9 - 9 + 04)^6 & & \\
 &:= (11 + 3 - 3 + 7 - 9 + 9 + 04)^6 & & \\
 &:= (11 - 3 + 3 + 7 - 9 + 9 + 04)^6 & & \\
 &:= (-1 + 13 + 3 - 7 + 9 + 9 - 04)^6 & & \\
 &:= (1 + 13 - 3 + 7 + 9 - 9 + 04)^6 & & \\
 &:= (1 + 13 - 3 + 7 - 9 + 9 + 04)^6 & & \\
 &:= (1 - 1 + 33 - 7 + 9 - 9 - 04)^6 & & \\
 &:= (-1 + 1 + 33 - 7 + 9 - 9 - 04)^6 & & \\
 &:= (1 - 1 + 33 - 7 - 9 + 9 - 04)^6 & & \\
 &:= (-1 + 1 + 33 - 7 - 9 + 9 - 04)^6 & & \\
 &:= (1 + 1 - 3 + 37 - 9 - 9 + 04)^6 & & \\
 &:= (113 - 3 + 7 - 99 + 04)^6 & & \\
 &:= (113 - 3 + 7 - 9 - 90 + 4)^6 & & \\
 & & & := (-11 - 33 + 79 - 9 - 04)^6 \\
 & & & := (-1 + 133 - 7 - 99 - 04)^6 \\
 & & & := (-1 + 133 - 7 - 9 - 90 - 4)^6 \\
 & & & := (-1 + 13 + 3 - 79 + 90 - 4)^6 \\
 \mathbf{114084125} &:= (11 + 408 + 41 + 25)^3 & & \\
 \mathbf{114791256} &:= (11 + 479 - 1 - 2 + 5 - 6)^3 & & \\
 &:= (-11 + 479 - 1 + 25 - 6)^3 & & \\
 \mathbf{115501303} &:= (1 - 15 + 501 + 3 - 03)^3 & & \\
 &:= (1 - 15 + 501 - 3 + 03)^3 & & \\
 \mathbf{115856201} &:= (-1 - 1 - 5 - 8 - 5 + 62 - 01)^5 & & \\
 &:= (-1 - 1 + 5 + 8 + 5 + 6 + 20 - 1)^5 & & \\
 &:= (-11 + 5 - 8 + 56 - 2 + 01)^5 & & \\
 &:= (115 - 8 - 5 - 62 + 01)^5 & & \\
 &:= (-1 + 15 - 8 + 56 - 20 - 1)^5 & & \\
 &:= (-1 - 158 + 5 - 6 + 201)^5 & & \\
 \mathbf{116208400} &:= (11620 - 840 + 0)^2 & & \\
 \mathbf{116214272} &:= (1 + 1 + 62 - 1 + 427 - 2)^3 & & \\
 &:= (1 - 1 + 62 + 1 + 427 - 2)^3 & & \\
 &:= (-1 + 1 + 62 + 1 + 427 - 2)^3 & & \\
 &:= (-1 - 1 + 62 - 1 + 427 + 2)^3 & & \\
 \mathbf{116985856} &:= (-1 - 1 + 6 + 98 + 5 + 8 - 5 - 6)^4 & & \\
 &:= (-1 - 1 + 6 + 98 - 5 + 8 + 5 - 6)^4 & & \\
 &:= (1 - 1 - 6 + 98 + 5 + 8 + 5 - 6)^4 & & \\
 &:= (-1 + 1 - 6 + 98 + 5 + 8 + 5 - 6)^4 & & \\
 &:= (1 + 1 + 6 + 98 + 5 - 8 - 5 + 6)^4 & & \\
 &:= (-1 - 1 - 6 + 98 + 5 + 8 - 5 + 6)^4 & & \\
 &:= (1 + 1 + 6 + 98 - 5 - 8 + 5 + 6)^4 & & \\
 &:= (-1 - 1 - 6 + 98 - 5 + 8 + 5 + 6)^4 & & \\
 &:= (11 + 6 + 9 + 85 - 8 - 5 + 6)^4 & & \\
 &:= (11 + 6 + 9 - 8 - 5 + 85 + 6)^4 & & \\
 &:= (1 + 16 + 9 + 85 - 8 - 5 + 6)^4 & & \\
 &:= (1 + 16 + 9 - 8 - 5 + 85 + 6)^4 & & \\
 &:= (1 - 1 + 69 - 8 - 5 - 8 + 56)^4 & & \\
 &:= (-1 + 1 + 69 - 8 - 5 - 8 + 56)^4 & & \\
 &:= (1 + 169 - 85 + 8 + 5 + 6)^4 & & \\
 &:= (1 + 169 + 8 + 5 - 85 + 6)^4 & & \\
 &:= (-1 - 1 + 69 + 85 + 8 - 56)^4 & & \\
 &:= (-1 - 1 + 6 + 98 + 58 - 56)^4 & &
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 &:= (1 + 1 + 6 + 98 - 58 + 56)^4 & &:= (12 + 6 + 2 + 4 + 7 + 69 + 6)^4 \\
 &:= (116 - 98 - 5 + 85 + 6)^4 & &:= (-1 + 26 - 2 + 4 + 76 + 9 - 6)^4 \\
 &:= (116 + 9 - 85 + 8 + 56)^4 & &:= (1 + 26 + 2 + 4 + 76 - 9 + 6)^4 \\
 \mathbf{117158976} &:= (11715 - 897 + 6)^2 & &:= (-1 + 26 + 2 - 4 - 7 - 6 + 96)^4 \\
 \mathbf{119049921} &:= (11904 - 992 - 1)^2 & &:= (-1 - 2 + 6 + 24 + 76 + 9 - 6)^4 \\
 \mathbf{119095488} &:= (-1 + 19 - 09 - 5 + 488)^3 & &:= (1 + 2 + 6 + 24 + 76 - 9 + 6)^4 \\
 \mathbf{120553784} &:= (120 + 5 - 5 + 378 - 4)^3 & &:= (-1 - 2 - 6 + 24 + 76 + 9 + 6)^4 \\
 &:= (120 - 5 + 5 + 378 - 4)^3 & &:= (126 - 24 + 7 - 6 + 9 - 6)^4 \\
 \mathbf{121110025} &:= (1 - 2 - 1 + 11002 + 5)^2 & &:= (-12 + 62 + 47 + 6 + 9 - 6)^4 \\
 &:= (-1 - 2 + 1 + 11002 + 5)^2 & &:= (-12 + 62 + 47 - 6 + 9 + 6)^4 \\
 \mathbf{121287375} &:= (121 - 2 + 8 - 7 + 375)^3 & &:= (-12 + 6 + 2 + 47 + 69 - 6)^4 \\
 &:= (1 - 2 + 128 - 7 + 375)^3 & &:= (-12 - 6 + 2 + 47 + 69 + 6)^4 \\
 \mathbf{121550625} &:= (1 + 2 - 15 + 50 + 62 + 5)^4 & &:= (-1 - 26 + 24 + 7 + 6 + 96)^4 \\
 \mathbf{122023936} &:= (1 + 220 + 239 + 36)^3 & &:= (-1 + 2 + 62 - 47 - 6 + 96)^4 \\
 \mathbf{122763473} &:= (12 + 2 + 7 + 6 - 3 + 473)^3 & & \mathbf{127263527} := (-12 - 7 - 2 - 6 + 3 + 527)^3 \\
 &:= (-12 + 27 + 6 + 3 + 473)^3 & & &:= (12 - 7 - 26 - 3 + 527)^3 \\
 &:= (-12 - 27 + 63 + 473)^3 & & \mathbf{128024064} := (12 + 80 + 2 + 406 + 4)^3 \\
 \mathbf{123121216} &:= (12312 - 1216)^2 & & \mathbf{128787625} := (-128 + 7 + 8 - 7 + 625)^3 \\
 \mathbf{123505992} &:= (12 - 3 + 505 - 9 - 9 + 2)^3 & & &:= (-128 - 7 + 8 + 7 + 625)^3 \\
 &:= (-12 + 3 + 505 + 9 - 9 + 2)^3 & & \mathbf{129140163} := (-1 + 2 + 9 - 1 + 4 - 01 - 6 - 3)^{17} \\
 &:= (-12 + 3 + 505 - 9 + 9 + 2)^3 & & &:= (1 - 2 + 9 + 1 + 4 - 01 - 6 - 3)^{17} \\
 &:= (-1 - 2 + 350 + 59 + 92)^3 & & &:= (1 - 2 + 9 - 1 + 4 + 01 - 6 - 3)^{17} \\
 \mathbf{124251499} &:= (-1 + 2 + 4 - 2 + 514 - 9 - 9)^3 & & &:= (-1 - 2 + 9 + 1 + 4 + 01 - 6 - 3)^{17} \\
 &:= (-1 - 2 + 4 + 2 + 514 - 9 - 9)^3 & & &:= (-1 - 2 + 9 - 1 - 4 - 01 + 6 - 3)^{17} \\
 &:= (12 - 4 - 2 - 5 - 1 + 499)^3 & & &:= (1 + 2 - 9 + 1 + 4 + 01 + 6 - 3)^{17} \\
 &:= (-12 + 4 + 2 + 5 + 1 + 499)^3 & & &:= (1 + 2 + 9 - 1 - 4 - 01 - 6 + 3)^{17} \\
 \mathbf{125751501} &:= (1 - 2 - 5 - 7 + 515 - 01)^3 & & &:= (-1 + 2 + 9 + 1 - 4 - 01 - 6 + 3)^{17} \\
 &:= (-1 - 2 - 5 - 7 + 515 + 01)^3 & & &:= (-1 + 2 + 9 - 1 - 4 + 01 - 6 + 3)^{17} \\
 \mathbf{126247696} &:= (1 + 2 + 6 + 2 + 4 + 76 + 9 + 6)^4 & & &:= (1 - 2 + 9 + 1 - 4 + 01 - 6 + 3)^{17} \\
 &:= (-1 + 2 + 6 - 2 + 4 + 7 - 6 + 96)^4 & & &:= (-1 + 2 - 9 - 1 + 4 - 01 + 6 + 3)^{17} \\
 &:= (-1 - 2 + 6 + 2 + 4 + 7 - 6 + 96)^4 & & &:= (1 - 2 - 9 + 1 + 4 - 01 + 6 + 3)^{17} \\
 &:= (1 + 2 + 6 - 2 + 4 - 7 + 6 + 96)^4 & & &:= (1 - 2 - 9 - 1 + 4 + 01 + 6 + 3)^{17} \\
 &:= (1 - 2 + 6 + 2 + 4 - 7 + 6 + 96)^4 & & &:= (-1 - 2 - 9 + 1 + 4 + 01 + 6 + 3)^{17} \\
 &:= (-1 - 2 + 6 - 2 - 4 + 7 + 6 + 96)^4 & & &:= (-12 + 9 + 14 + 01 - 6 - 3)^{17} \\
 &:= (-1 + 2 - 6 - 2 + 4 + 7 + 6 + 96)^4 & & &:= (12 + 9 - 14 - 01 - 6 + 3)^{17} \\
 &:= (-1 - 2 - 6 + 2 + 4 + 7 + 6 + 96)^4 & & &:= (-12 - 9 + 14 + 01 + 6 + 3)^{17} \\
 &:= (126 - 2 - 4 + 7 - 6 - 9 - 6)^4 & & &:= (12 + 9 - 1 - 4 - 016 + 3)^{17} \\
 &:= (12 + 62 + 4 + 7 + 6 + 9 + 6)^4 & & &:= (-12 - 9 + 1 + 4 + 016 + 3)^{17}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 &:= (1 - 29 + 1 + 40 - 1 - 6 - 3)^{17} & &:= (-1 + 31 + 07 + 9 + 60 + 1)^4 \\
 &:= (1 - 29 - 1 + 40 + 1 - 6 - 3)^{17} & &:= (1 - 3 + 107 + 9 - 6 - 01)^4 \\
 &:= (-1 - 29 + 1 + 40 + 1 - 6 - 3)^{17} & &:= (1 + 3 + 107 - 9 + 6 - 01)^4 \\
 &:= (1 - 2 + 9 + 14 - 016 - 3)^{17} & &:= (-1 - 3 + 107 + 9 - 6 + 01)^4 \\
 &:= (1 + 29 - 14 - 016 + 3)^{17} & &:= (-1 + 3 + 107 - 9 + 6 + 01)^4 \\
 &:= (-1 - 29 + 14 + 016 + 3)^{17} & &:= (13 + 10 + 79 + 6 - 01)^4 \\
 &:= (-1 + 29 - 1 + 40 - 1 - 63)^{17} & &:= (13 - 10 + 7 + 96 + 01)^4 \\
 &:= (-129 + 140 + 1 - 6 - 3)^{17} & & \\
 \mathbf{129554216} &:= (-1 + 2 + 95 - 5 + 421 - 6)^3 & \mathbf{131096512} &:= (1 - 3 + 1 - 09 + 6 + 512)^3 \\
 &:= (-12 - 9 + 554 - 21 - 6)^3 & \mathbf{132618256} &:= (-1 + 3261 + 8256)^2 \\
 &:= (-1 - 29 + 554 - 2 - 16)^3 & \mathbf{132651000} &:= (1 + 3 + 2 - 6 + 510 + 00)^3 \\
 & & &:= (-1 - 3 - 2 + 6 + 510 + 00)^3 \\
 \mathbf{130323843} &:= (-13 - 0323 + 843)^3 & \mathbf{133432831} &:= (1 - 3 - 3 + 432 + 83 + 1)^3 \\
 & & &:= (-1 + 3343 - 2831)^3 \\
 \mathbf{130691232} &:= (1 + 30 + 6 + 9 - 1 + 2 - 3 - 2)^5 & \mathbf{134217728} &:= (13 + 4 + 2 - 1 + 7 - 7 - 2 - 8)^9 \\
 &:= (-1 + 30 + 6 + 9 + 1 + 2 - 3 - 2)^5 & &:= (13 - 4 + 2 + 1 + 7 - 7 - 2 - 8)^{27} \\
 &:= (-1 + 30 + 6 + 9 - 1 - 2 + 3 - 2)^5 & &:= (13 + 4 + 2 - 1 - 7 + 7 - 2 - 8)^9 \\
 &:= (1 + 30 + 6 + 9 - 1 - 2 - 3 + 2)^5 & &:= (13 - 4 + 2 + 1 - 7 + 7 - 2 - 8)^{27} \\
 &:= (-1 + 30 + 6 + 9 + 1 - 2 - 3 + 2)^5 & &:= (13 + 4 - 2 - 1 + 7 - 7 + 2 - 8)^9 \\
 &:= (1 + 30 - 6 + 9 + 1 + 2 + 3 + 2)^5 & &:= (13 - 4 - 2 + 1 + 7 - 7 + 2 - 8)^{27} \\
 &:= (1 - 3 + 06 + 9 - 1 - 2 + 32)^5 & &:= (13 + 4 - 2 - 1 - 7 + 7 + 2 - 8)^9 \\
 &:= (-1 - 3 + 06 + 9 + 1 - 2 + 32)^5 & &:= (13 - 4 - 2 + 1 - 7 + 7 + 2 - 8)^{27} \\
 &:= (1 + 3 - 06 + 9 + 1 + 2 + 32)^5 & &:= (13 + 4 - 2 - 1 - 7 + 7 + 2 - 8)^9 \\
 &:= (13 - 06 + 9 + 1 + 23 + 2)^5 & &:= (13 - 4 - 2 + 1 - 7 + 7 + 2 - 8)^{27} \\
 &:= (1 - 30 + 69 - 1 + 2 + 3 - 2)^5 & &:= (13 - 4 + 2 - 1 - 7 - 7 - 2 + 8)^{27} \\
 &:= (-1 - 30 + 69 + 1 + 2 + 3 - 2)^5 & &:= (13 + 4 - 2 + 1 - 7 - 7 - 2 + 8)^9 \\
 &:= (1 - 30 + 69 + 1 + 2 - 3 + 2)^5 & &:= (-13 + 4 - 2 - 1 + 7 + 7 - 2 + 8)^9 \\
 &:= (1 - 30 + 69 - 1 - 2 + 3 + 2)^5 & &:= (-13 - 4 - 2 + 1 + 7 + 7 - 2 + 8)^{27} \\
 &:= (-1 - 30 + 69 + 1 - 2 + 3 + 2)^5 & &:= (13 - 4 - 2 - 1 - 7 - 7 + 2 + 8)^{27} \\
 &:= (1 + 30 - 6 - 9 + 1 + 23 + 2)^5 & &:= (13 - 4 + 2 + 1 - 7 - 7 + 2 + 8)^9 \\
 &:= (1 + 3 + 069 - 1 + 2 - 32)^5 & &:= (-13 + 4 + 2 - 1 + 7 - 7 + 2 + 8)^{27} \\
 &:= (-1 + 3 + 069 + 1 + 2 - 32)^5 & &:= (-13 + 4 + 2 - 1 - 7 + 7 + 2 + 8)^{27} \\
 &:= (130 + 6 - 91 + 2 - 3 - 2)^5 & &:= (-13 - 4 + 2 - 1 + 7 + 7 + 2 + 8)^9 \\
 &:= (130 + 6 - 91 - 2 - 3 + 2)^5 & &:= (1 + 34 - 2 - 1 - 7 - 7 - 2 - 8)^9 \\
 &:= (-13 - 06 + 91 + 2 - 32)^5 & &:= (-1 + 34 - 2 + 1 - 7 - 7 - 2 - 8)^9 \\
 &:= (13 - 06 - 9 + 12 + 32)^5 & &:= (1 + 3 - 4 + 2 + 17 - 7 - 2 - 8)^{27} \\
 \mathbf{131079601} &:= (1 + 3 + 1 + 07 + 96 - 01)^4 & &:= (-1 - 3 + 4 + 2 + 17 - 7 - 2 - 8)^{27} \\
 &:= (1 + 3 - 1 + 07 + 96 + 01)^4 & &:= (-1 + 3 + 4 + 2 + 17 - 7 - 2 - 8)^9 \\
 &:= (-1 + 3 + 1 + 07 + 96 + 01)^4 & &:= (-1 - 3 - 4 + 2 + 17 + 7 - 2 - 8)^9 \\
 &:= (1 + 31 + 07 + 9 + 60 - 1)^4 & &:= (1 + 3 - 4 - 2 + 17 - 7 + 2 - 8)^{27}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 &:= (-1-3+4-2+17-7+2-8)^{27} & &:= (1+3-4-2-17-7+28)^{27} \\
 &:= (-1+3+4-2+17-7+2-8)^9 & &:= (-1-3+4-2-17-7+28)^{27} \\
 &:= (1-3+4+2+17-7+2-8)^9 & &:= (-1+3+4-2-17-7+28)^9 \\
 &:= (-1-3-4-2+17+7+2-8)^9 & &:= (1-3+4+2-17-7+28)^9 \\
 &:= (1-3-4-2+17-7-2+8)^9 & &:= (-1-3-4-2-17+7+28)^9 \\
 &:= (1+3+4-2-17+7-2+8)^{27} & &:= (-13+42+1+7-7-28)^{27} \\
 &:= (1+3-4+2-17+7+2+8)^{27} & &:= (-13+42+1-7+7-28)^{27} \\
 &:= (-1-3+4+2-17+7+2+8)^{27} & &:= (13-4+21+7-7-28)^{27} \\
 &:= (-1+3+4+2-17+7+2+8)^9 & &:= (13-4+21-7+7-28)^{27} \\
 &:= (-13+42-1-7-7+2-8)^9 & &:= (13-4-21-7-7+28)^{27} \\
 &:= (-13+4+21+7-7-2-8)^{27} & &:= (1-34+21-7-7+28)^{27} \\
 &:= (-13+4+21-7+7-2-8)^{27} & &:= (1+3+421+77+2+8)^3 \\
 &:= (-13-4+21+7+7-2-8)^9 & &:= (1+3+421+7+72+8)^3 \\
 &:= (13+4-21+7-7-2+8)^{27} & &:= (1-3+42-17+7-28)^{27} \\
 &:= (13+4-21-7+7-2+8)^{27} & &:= (1+3+42-17+7-28)^9 \\
 &:= (13-4-21+7+7-2+8)^9 & &:= (1-3-42+17+7+28)^9 \\
 &:= (-13+4+21-7-7+2+8)^9 & &:= (-1-3-42-1+77-28)^{27} \\
 &:= (13+4-2+1+7+7-28)^{27} & &:= (-1+3-42-1+77-28)^9 \\
 &:= (-13+4-2-1-7-7+28)^{27} & &:= (13+42+17-72+8)^9 \\
 &:= (-13+4+2+1-7-7+28)^9 & &:= (-13-42-17+72+8)^9 \\
 &:= (-13-4-2-1+7-7+28)^9 & &:= (-1+342+177+2-8)^3 \\
 &:= (-13-4-2-1-7+7+28)^9 & &:= (134-21-77-28)^9 \\
 &:= (-1+34-21+7-7-2-8)^{27} & & \mathbf{135005697} := (1+3+500+5+6-9+7)^3 \\
 &:= (-1+34-21-7+7-2-8)^{27} & &:= (1-3+500+5-6+9+7)^3 \\
 &:= (1+34-21+7-7+2-8)^9 & &:= (-1-3+500-5+6+9+7)^3 \\
 &:= (1+34-21-7+7+2-8)^9 & &:= (-13-50+0569+7)^3 \\
 &:= (1-34+21+7+7-2+8)^9 & & \mathbf{135796744} := (-1+3+579-67+4-4)^3 \\
 &:= (-1+34-21-7-7+2+8)^9 & &:= (-1+3+579-67-4+4)^3 \\
 &:= (-1+34-2-1+7-7-28)^{27} & & \mathbf{136048896} := (-1+3+6+04+8-8+96)^4 \\
 &:= (1+34+2-1+7-7-28)^9 & &:= (-1+3+6+04-8+8+96)^4 \\
 &:= (-1+34+2+1+7-7-28)^9 & &:= (1-3-6+04+8+8+96)^4 \\
 &:= (-1+34-2-1-7+7-28)^{27} & &:= (13+60+4+8+8+9+6)^4 \\
 &:= (1+34+2-1-7+7-28)^9 & &:= (13+6+04+88-9+6)^4 \\
 &:= (-1+34+2+1-7+7-28)^9 & &:= (1+36+048+8+9+6)^4 \\
 &:= (-1-34+2-1+7+7+28)^9 & &:= (1+36-04-8+89-6)^4 \\
 &:= (1-34-2+1+7+7+28)^9 & &:= (1-36+048+89+6)^4 \\
 &:= (-1-3+42-17-7+2-8)^9 & &:= (13+60-48+89-6)^4 \\
 &:= (1+3+4-2+17+7-28)^{27} & & \mathbf{136590875} := (-1+3+6+590-8-75)^3
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 &:= (1 - 3 - 6 + 590 + 8 - 75)^3 \\
 &:= (13 - 6 + 590 - 87 + 5)^3 \\
 \mathbf{138188413} &:= (1 - 381 + 884 + 13)^3 \\
 \mathbf{139617856} &:= (-1 + 3961 + 7856)^2 \\
 \mathbf{141158161} &:= (14 + 1 + 1 + 5 + 81 + 6 + 1)^4 \\
 &:= (1 + 41 + 1 + 58 + 1 + 6 + 1)^4 \\
 &:= (1 + 4 + 11 + 5 + 81 + 6 + 1)^4 \\
 &:= (1 + 4 + 1 + 15 + 81 + 6 + 1)^4 \\
 &:= (1 + 41 + 15 - 8 - 1 + 61)^4 \\
 &:= (-1 + 41 + 15 - 8 + 1 + 61)^4 \\
 &:= (1 - 41 + 1 - 5 - 8 + 161)^4 \\
 &:= (-1 + 4 + 115 + 8 - 16 - 1)^4 \\
 &:= (14 - 1 + 158 - 1 - 61)^4 \\
 &:= (-1 - 4 + 11 - 58 + 161)^4 \\
 &:= (14 + 115 - 81 + 61)^4 \\
 \mathbf{142236648} &:= (142 + 2 + 366 + 4 + 8)^3 \\
 \mathbf{143877824} &:= (-1 + 438 + 77 + 8 - 2 + 4)^3 \\
 &:= (-1 + 438 + 7 + 78 - 2 + 4)^3 \\
 \mathbf{145531576} &:= (-14 + 5 + 531 + 5 - 7 + 6)^3 \\
 &:= (-1 + 4 - 55 + 3 - 1 + 576)^3 \\
 &:= (1 - 4 + 5 - 53 + 1 + 576)^3 \\
 &:= (1 + 45 + 531 - 57 + 6)^3 \\
 \mathbf{146363183} &:= (1 + 4 + 636 - 31 - 83)^3 \\
 \mathbf{147008443} &:= (-1 + 47 + 008 - 4 - 4 - 3)^5 \\
 &:= (-1 + 47 - 008 + 4 + 4 - 3)^5 \\
 &:= (1 + 47 - 008 + 4 - 4 + 3)^5 \\
 &:= (1 + 47 - 008 - 4 + 4 + 3)^5 \\
 &:= (-1 + 4 + 7 - 008 + 44 - 3)^5 \\
 &:= (1 - 4 + 7 - 008 + 44 + 3)^5 \\
 &:= (-1 - 4 - 7 + 008 + 44 + 3)^5 \\
 &:= (1 + 4 + 7 - 008 - 4 + 43)^5 \\
 &:= (-1 + 4 - 7 + 008 - 4 + 43)^5 \\
 &:= (1 - 4 + 7 - 008 + 4 + 43)^5 \\
 &:= (-1 - 4 - 7 + 008 + 4 + 43)^5 \\
 &:= (-14 + 70 - 08 - 4 - 4 + 3)^5 \\
 &:= (-1 - 47 + 0084 + 4 + 3)^5 \\
 &:= (-1 - 4 + 7 + 0084 - 43)^5 \\
 &:= (14 + 70 - 084 + 43)^5 \\
 &:= (-14 - 70 + 084 + 43)^5 \\
 \mathbf{148035889} &:= (14 + 8 + 03 + 5 - 8 - 8 + 9)^6 \\
 &:= (14 + 8 - 03 - 5 + 8 - 8 + 9)^6 \\
 &:= (14 - 8 + 03 + 5 + 8 - 8 + 9)^6 \\
 &:= (14 + 8 - 03 - 5 - 8 + 8 + 9)^6 \\
 &:= (14 - 8 + 03 + 5 - 8 + 8 + 9)^6 \\
 &:= (14 - 8 - 03 - 5 + 8 + 8 + 9)^6 \\
 &:= (1 + 4 + 8 + 035 - 8 - 8 - 9)^6 \\
 &:= (1 + 4 - 8 + 035 + 8 - 8 - 9)^6 \\
 &:= (1 + 4 - 8 + 035 - 8 + 8 - 9)^6 \\
 &:= (-1 + 4 - 8 + 035 - 8 - 8 + 9)^6 \\
 &:= (1 + 48 - 035 + 8 - 8 + 9)^6 \\
 &:= (1 + 48 - 035 - 8 + 8 + 9)^6 \\
 &:= (-1 - 48 - 03 + 58 + 8 + 9)^6 \\
 &:= (-1 + 4 + 80 - 35 - 8 - 8 - 9)^6 \\
 &:= (1 + 4 + 80 - 3 - 58 + 8 - 9)^6 \\
 &:= (-1 + 4 + 80 - 3 - 58 - 8 + 9)^6 \\
 &:= (1 - 4 + 80 + 3 - 58 - 8 + 9)^6 \\
 &:= (-1 + 4 - 8 - 03 - 58 + 89)^6 \\
 &:= (1 - 4 - 8 + 03 - 58 + 89)^6 \\
 &:= (14 + 80 + 3 + 5 - 88 + 9)^6 \\
 &:= (14 - 80 - 3 - 5 + 88 + 9)^6 \\
 &:= (14 - 80 + 3 + 5 - 8 + 89)^6 \\
 &:= (14 - 80 - 3 - 5 + 8 + 89)^6 \\
 &:= (1 - 48 - 03 + 588 - 9)^3 \\
 &:= (1 + 4 + 80 + 35 - 88 - 9)^6 \\
 &:= (1 + 4 + 80 + 35 - 8 - 89)^6 \\
 \mathbf{149377284} &:= (1 + 4937 + 7284)^2 \\
 \mathbf{149721291} &:= (1 + 497 + 21 + 2 + 9 + 1)^3 \\
 &:= (1 + 497 + 2 + 1 + 29 + 1)^3 \\
 \mathbf{150568768} &:= (-15 + 0568 - 7 - 6 - 8)^3 \\
 \mathbf{151419437} &:= (1 + 514 + 1 + 9 + 4 - 3 + 7)^3 \\
 \mathbf{151807041} &:= (1 + 51 - 8 + 070 - 4 + 1)^4 \\
 &:= (1 - 5 + 1 + 80 - 7 + 041)^4 \\
 &:= (151 + 8 - 07 - 041)^4 \\
 &:= (1 + 5 + 180 - 70 - 4 - 1)^4 \\
 &:= (-1 + 5 + 180 - 70 - 4 + 1)^4 \\
 &:= (1 - 5 + 180 - 70 + 4 + 1)^4
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 \mathbf{152273304} &:= (1 + 522 + 7 + 3 - 3 + 04)^3 & := (-1 + 583 - 40 - 4 + 2 + 1)^3 \\
 &:= (1 + 522 + 7 - 3 + 3 + 04)^3 & := (158 + 340 + 42 + 1)^3 \\
 &:= (1 + 5 + 227 - 3 + 304)^3 & \\
 \mathbf{153990656} &:= (1 + 539 - 9 + 06 + 5 - 6)^3 & \mathbf{160989184} := (1 + 609 + 8 + 9 + 1 - 84)^3 \\
 &:= (-1 + 539 - 9 + 06 - 5 + 6)^3 & \mathbf{161878625} := (-1 + 618 + 7 - 86 + 2 + 5)^3 \\
 &:= (1 + 539 - 9 - 06 + 5 + 6)^3 & := (-1 + 618 - 7 - 8 - 62 + 5)^3 \\
 & \\
 \mathbf{154854153} &:= (-1 + 548 - 5 + 4 - 1 - 5 - 3)^3 & := (1 + 6 - 1 - 8 - 78 + 625)^3 \\
 &:= (1 + 548 - 5 - 4 - 1 - 5 + 3)^3 & := (-1 + 6 + 1 - 8 - 78 + 625)^3 \\
 &:= (-1 + 548 - 5 - 4 + 1 - 5 + 3)^3 & := (16 - 1 - 87 - 8 + 625)^3 \\
 &:= (1 + 5 - 4 - 8 + 541 + 5 - 3)^3 & := (16 - 18 - 78 + 625)^3 \\
 &:= (-1 - 5 - 4 + 8 + 541 - 5 + 3)^3 & \mathbf{161976529} := (1 + 6197 + 6529)^2 \\
 &:= (-1 + 5 + 485 - 4 - 1 + 53)^3 & \mathbf{163047361} := (1 + 63 + 047 - 3 + 6 - 1)^4 \\
 &:= (1 - 5 + 485 + 4 - 1 + 53)^3 & := (-1 + 63 + 047 - 3 + 6 + 1)^4 \\
 &:= (-1 - 5 + 485 + 4 + 1 + 53)^3 & := (1 + 6 + 30 - 4 + 73 + 6 + 1)^4 \\
 & \\
 \mathbf{156125025} &:= (-1 + 5 - 6 + 12502 - 5)^2 & := (-1 + 6 + 3 + 047 - 3 + 61)^4 \\
 &:= (-1 - 5 - 6 + 12502 + 5)^2 & := (-1 + 6 - 3 + 047 + 3 + 61)^4 \\
 & \\
 \mathbf{156590819} &:= (1 + 565 - 9 - 08 - 1 - 9)^3 & := (16 + 30 - 4 + 7 + 3 + 61)^4 \\
 &:= (-1 + 565 - 9 - 08 + 1 - 9)^3 & := (-1 + 6 - 30 + 4 + 73 + 61)^4 \\
 &:= (15 + 6 + 590 - 81 + 9)^3 & \\
 & \\
 \mathbf{157351936} &:= (15 + 73 + 5 + 1 + 9 + 3 + 6)^4 & \mathbf{163667323} := (1 + 636 + 6 - 73 - 23)^3 \\
 &:= (15 + 7 - 3 + 5 + 1 + 93 - 6)^4 & := (163 - 6 + 67 + 323)^3 \\
 &:= (15 + 7 - 3 - 5 - 1 + 93 + 6)^4 & \mathbf{164566592} := (-16 + 4 + 566 + 5 - 9 - 2)^3 \\
 &:= (1 + 57 + 35 + 1 + 9 + 3 + 6)^4 & := (-16 - 4 + 566 - 5 + 9 - 2)^3 \\
 &:= (1 + 57 + 3 + 51 + 9 - 3 - 6)^4 & := (16 + 456 + 65 + 9 + 2)^3 \\
 &:= (1 + 57 - 3 + 51 + 9 + 3 - 6)^4 & := (-16 - 4 - 5 + 665 - 92)^3 \\
 &:= (1 + 57 + 3 + 51 - 9 + 3 + 6)^4 & \mathbf{164916224} := (16 + 4 + 9 + 1 + 6 + 2 + 2 + 4)^5 \\
 &:= (1 + 57 + 3 + 5 + 1 + 9 + 36)^4 & := (1 + 6 + 4 + 9 + 16 + 2 + 2 + 4)^5 \\
 &:= (1 + 5 + 73 + 51 - 9 - 3 - 6)^4 & := (-16 + 49 + 1 + 6 + 2 - 2 + 4)^5 \\
 &:= (-1 - 5 + 73 + 51 - 9 - 3 + 6)^4 & := (-16 + 49 + 1 + 6 - 2 + 2 + 4)^5 \\
 &:= (1 + 5 + 73 + 5 + 19 + 3 + 6)^4 & := (-16 - 4 + 9 - 1 + 62 - 2 - 4)^5 \\
 &:= (1 + 5 + 73 + 5 + 1 - 9 + 36)^4 & := (-16 + 4 - 9 + 1 + 62 - 2 + 4)^5 \\
 &:= (1 - 5 - 7 + 35 + 1 + 93 - 6)^4 & := (16 - 4 + 9 - 1 + 6 + 22 - 4)^5 \\
 &:= (1 + 5 + 7 + 3 + 51 + 9 + 36)^4 & := (16 + 4 - 9 + 1 + 6 + 22 + 4)^5 \\
 &:= (157 - 35 - 19 + 3 + 6)^4 & := (16 + 4 + 9 - 1 - 6 - 2 + 24)^5 \\
 &:= (157 + 3 + 51 - 93 - 6)^4 & := (16 + 4 - 9 + 1 + 6 + 2 + 24)^5 \\
 &:= (15 + 73 + 51 + 9 - 36)^4 & := (1 + 64 - 9 - 16 + 2 - 2 + 4)^5 \\
 &:= (15 + 7 + 35 + 19 + 36)^4 & := (1 + 64 - 9 - 16 - 2 + 2 + 4)^5 \\
 & \\
 \mathbf{158340421} &:= (1 + 583 - 40 - 4 + 2 - 1)^3 & := (1 + 6 + 49 - 16 + 2 - 2 + 4)^5 \\
 & & := (1 + 6 + 49 - 16 - 2 + 2 + 4)^5 \\
 & & := (-1 + 6 + 4 + 91 - 62 + 2 + 4)^5
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 &:= (-1 + 6 - 4 + 9 + 16 + 22 - 4)^5 \\
 &:= (1 + 6 + 4 - 9 + 16 + 22 + 4)^5 \\
 &:= (-1 - 6 + 4 + 9 + 16 - 2 + 24)^5 \\
 &:= (1 + 6 + 4 - 9 + 16 + 2 + 24)^5 \\
 &:= (16 + 49 - 1 + 6 - 22 - 4)^5 \\
 &:= (-16 + 49 - 1 - 6 + 22 - 4)^5 \\
 &:= (16 + 49 - 1 + 6 - 2 - 24)^5 \\
 &:= (1 - 64 + 91 - 6 - 2 + 24)^5 \\
 &:= (-1 + 64 - 9 + 16 - 22 - 4)^5 \\
 &:= (-1 + 64 - 9 + 16 - 2 - 24)^5 \\
 &:= (-1 + 6 + 49 + 16 - 22 - 4)^5 \\
 &:= (-1 - 6 + 49 - 16 + 22 - 4)^5 \\
 &:= (-1 + 6 + 49 + 16 - 2 - 24)^5 \\
 &:= (1 - 6 - 4 + 91 - 62 + 24)^5 \\
 &:= (-164 - 9 - 1 - 6 + 224)^5 \\
 \mathbf{165469149} &:= (16 + 546 - 9 + 1 + 4 - 9)^3 \\
 &:= (1 + 65 + 469 + 1 + 4 + 9)^3 \\
 &:= (1 + 6 + 546 - 9 + 14 - 9)^3 \\
 \mathbf{166375000} &:= (1 + 6 + 6 + 37 + 500 + 0)^3 \\
 \mathbf{168196608} &:= (-1 - 68 + 19 - 6 + 608)^3 \\
 \mathbf{168896016} &:= (1 + 6 + 8 + 8 + 96 + 01 - 6)^4 \\
 &:= (1 - 6 + 8 + 8 + 96 + 01 + 6)^4 \\
 &:= (16 + 88 + 9 + 6 + 01 - 6)^4 \\
 &:= (16 + 88 + 9 - 6 + 01 + 6)^4 \\
 &:= (16 + 8 + 89 + 6 + 01 - 6)^4 \\
 &:= (16 + 8 + 89 - 6 + 01 + 6)^4 \\
 &:= (1 + 6 + 88 + 9 - 6 + 016)^4 \\
 &:= (1 - 6 + 88 + 9 + 6 + 016)^4 \\
 &:= (1 + 6 + 8 + 89 - 6 + 016)^4 \\
 &:= (1 - 6 + 8 + 89 + 6 + 016)^4 \\
 &:= (168 - 8 + 9 - 60 - 1 + 6)^4 \\
 &:= (168 + 8 - 9 - 60 + 1 + 6)^4 \\
 &:= (1 + 68 - 8 + 9 + 60 - 16)^4 \\
 &:= (1 + 68 + 89 - 60 + 16)^4 \\
 \mathbf{169112377} &:= (-1 + 691 - 123 - 7 - 7)^3 \\
 \mathbf{169130025} &:= (1 + 6 - 9 + 13002 + 5)^2 \\
 \mathbf{170031464} &:= (1 + 700 + 3 - 146 - 4)^3 \\
 &:= (-1 + 700 - 3 - 146 + 4)^3 \\
 \mathbf{170859375} &:= (1 + 7 + 08 + 5 + 9 - 3 - 7 - 5)^7 \\
 &:= (1 - 7 + 08 + 5 + 9 - 3 + 7 - 5)^7 \\
 &:= (-1 + 7 + 08 + 5 - 9 + 3 + 7 - 5)^7 \\
 &:= (1 + 7 + 08 - 5 + 9 - 3 - 7 + 5)^7 \\
 &:= (1 + 7 - 08 + 5 + 9 + 3 - 7 + 5)^7 \\
 &:= (-1 - 7 + 08 + 5 + 9 + 3 - 7 + 5)^7 \\
 &:= (1 - 7 + 08 - 5 + 9 - 3 + 7 + 5)^7 \\
 &:= (-1 + 7 + 08 - 5 - 9 + 3 + 7 + 5)^7 \\
 &:= (1 - 7 - 08 + 5 + 9 + 3 + 7 + 5)^7 \\
 &:= (1 + 70 + 8 - 59 - 3 - 7 + 5)^7 \\
 &:= (1 - 70 + 8 - 5 + 93 - 7 - 5)^7 \\
 &:= (-1 + 70 - 8 + 5 - 9 - 37 - 5)^7 \\
 &:= (-1 + 70 - 8 - 5 - 9 - 37 + 5)^7 \\
 &:= (1 + 70 + 8 + 5 + 9 - 3 - 75)^7 \\
 &:= (1 - 70 + 8 - 5 + 9 - 3 + 75)^7 \\
 &:= (1 - 70 - 8 + 5 + 9 + 3 + 75)^7 \\
 &:= (-1 + 7 - 08 + 59 - 37 - 5)^7 \\
 &:= (1 - 7 + 08 - 59 - 3 + 75)^7 \\
 &:= (1 - 7 + 08 - 5 + 93 - 75)^7 \\
 &:= (17 + 085 - 9 - 3 - 75)^7 \\
 &:= (170 + 8 + 5 - 93 - 75)^7 \\
 \mathbf{170953875} &:= (-1 + 7 + 09 + 538 + 7 - 5)^3 \\
 \mathbf{171879616} &:= (1 - 71 + 8 - 7 + 9 + 616)^3 \\
 &:= (17 + 1 - 87 + 9 + 616)^3 \\
 \mathbf{172213129} &:= (1 - 7 + 2 - 2 + 13129)^2 \\
 &:= (1 - 7 - 2 + 2 + 13129)^2 \\
 \mathbf{174676879} &:= (1 + 7 + 467 + 68 + 7 + 9)^3 \\
 &:= (1 + 7 + 467 + 6 + 87 - 9)^3 \\
 &:= (-17 - 4 + 676 - 87 - 9)^3 \\
 \mathbf{174900625} &:= (1 + 7 + 4 + 90 + 06 + 2 + 5)^4 \\
 &:= (1 + 74 + 9 + 006 + 25)^4 \\
 &:= (174 - 90 + 06 + 25)^4 \\
 \mathbf{175616000} &:= (17 - 56 - 1 + 600 + 0)^3 \\
 \mathbf{176558481} &:= (-1 + 7 - 6 + 558 - 4 + 8 - 1)^3 \\
 &:= (1 - 7 + 6 + 558 - 4 + 8 - 1)^3 \\
 &:= (1 + 7 + 6 + 558 - 4 - 8 + 1)^3 \\
 &:= (-1 - 7 + 6 + 558 - 4 + 8 + 1)^3 \\
 &:= (-17 + 6 - 5 + 584 - 8 + 1)^3
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 & := (-17 + 655 - 84 + 8 - 1)^3 & := (-18 - 4 - 5 - 2 + 81 - 2 - 5)^5 \\
 & := (-17 + 655 + 8 - 4 - 81)^3 & := (18 + 4 + 5 + 2 - 8 - 1 + 25)^5 \\
 \mathbf{177715561} & := (-1 + 7771 + 5561)^2 & := (18 - 4 - 5 + 2 + 8 + 1 + 25)^5 \\
 \mathbf{177795556} & := (-1 + 7779 + 5556)^2 & := (1 + 84 - 52 + 8 + 1 - 2 + 5)^5 \\
 \mathbf{178453547} & := (-1 + 7 + 8 + 4 - 5 + 3 + 547)^3 & := (-1 + 84 - 52 + 8 - 1 + 2 + 5)^5 \\
 & := (1 + 78 - 4 + 535 - 47)^3 & := (-1 + 8 + 45 + 2 + 8 - 12 - 5)^5 \\
 \mathbf{180714249} & := (1 - 807 + 14249)^2 & := (1 - 8 + 45 - 2 - 8 + 12 + 5)^5 \\
 \mathbf{181063936} & := (1 + 8 - 1 + 06 + 3 + 93 + 6)^4 & := (1 + 8 + 4 - 52 + 81 - 2 + 5)^5 \\
 & := (-1 + 8 + 1 + 06 + 3 + 93 + 6)^4 & := (-1 + 8 + 4 + 52 + 8 - 1 - 25)^5 \\
 & := (-1 + 81 + 06 + 39 - 3 - 6)^4 & := (1 + 8 - 4 + 5 + 28 + 12 - 5)^5 \\
 & := (-1 + 81 - 06 + 39 - 3 + 6)^4 & := (1 + 8 - 4 - 5 + 28 + 12 + 5)^5 \\
 & := (-1 + 81 + 06 + 3 - 9 + 36)^4 & := (-1 - 8 + 4 + 5 + 28 + 12 + 5)^5 \\
 & := (-1 + 81 - 06 - 3 + 9 + 36)^4 & := (18 - 45 - 2 + 81 - 2 - 5)^5 \\
 & := (-1 + 8 + 106 + 3 + 9 - 3 - 6)^4 & := (18 + 45 - 2 + 8 + 1 - 25)^5 \\
 & := (-1 + 8 + 106 - 3 + 9 + 3 - 6)^4 & := (-18 + 45 + 2 - 8 - 1 + 25)^5 \\
 & := (-1 + 8 + 106 + 3 - 9 + 3 + 6)^4 & := (-18 - 4 + 52 + 8 + 12 - 5)^5 \\
 & := (1 + 8 - 1 + 063 + 9 + 36)^4 & := (-18 + 4 + 5 + 28 + 1 + 25)^5 \\
 & := (-1 + 8 + 1 + 063 + 9 + 36)^4 & := (-18 + 4 + 5 - 2 + 81 - 25)^5 \\
 & := (18 - 10 + 6 + 3 + 93 + 6)^4 & := (-1 - 84 + 52 + 81 + 2 - 5)^5 \\
 & := (-1 + 81 - 063 + 93 + 6)^4 & := (1 + 84 + 5 - 28 - 12 - 5)^5 \\
 & := (-1 + 81 + 063 + 9 - 36)^4 & := (1 + 84 - 5 - 28 - 12 + 5)^5 \\
 & := (18 - 10 + 63 + 9 + 36)^4 & := (-1 - 84 - 5 + 2 + 8 + 125)^5 \\
 & := (-1 - 810 - 6 - 3 + 936)^4 & := (-18 - 45 + 2 + 81 + 25)^5 \\
 & := (-1 + 8 + 106 + 39 - 36)^4 & := (1 - 8 - 45 - 28 + 125)^5 \\
 \mathbf{182284263} & := (18 + 2 + 284 + 263)^3 & \mathbf{186513649} & := (-1 + 8 + 6 - 5 + 13649)^2 \\
 & & & := (1 + 8 - 6 + 5 + 13649)^2 \\
 \mathbf{183250432} & := (1 + 83 + 2 + 50 + 432)^3 & & \\
 \mathbf{184528125} & := (18 + 4 + 5 + 2 + 8 + 1 + 2 + 5)^5 & \mathbf{187388721} & := (1 + 87 + 3 + 8 + 8 + 7 + 2 + 1)^4 \\
 & := (1 + 8 - 4 + 52 - 8 - 1 + 2 - 5)^5 & & := (1 + 8 + 7 + 3 + 88 + 7 + 2 + 1)^4 \\
 & := (1 - 8 - 4 + 52 + 8 - 1 + 2 - 5)^5 & & := (1 + 8 + 7 + 3 + 8 + 87 + 2 + 1)^4 \\
 & := (-1 + 8 - 4 + 52 - 8 + 1 + 2 - 5)^5 & & := (18 + 73 + 8 + 8 + 7 + 2 + 1)^4 \\
 & := (-1 - 8 - 4 + 52 + 8 + 1 + 2 - 5)^5 & & := (18 + 7 + 3 + 8 + 8 + 72 + 1)^4 \\
 & := (1 - 8 + 4 + 52 - 8 + 1 - 2 + 5)^5 & & := (-1 + 87 + 3 + 8 - 8 + 7 + 21)^4 \\
 & := (-1 - 8 + 4 + 52 - 8 - 1 + 2 + 5)^5 & & := (-1 + 87 + 3 - 8 + 8 + 7 + 21)^4 \\
 & := (1 + 8 + 4 + 5 + 2 + 8 + 12 + 5)^5 & & := (1 + 8 + 7 + 38 - 8 + 72 - 1)^4 \\
 & := (18 + 45 - 2 - 8 - 1 - 2 - 5)^5 & & := (-1 + 8 - 7 + 38 + 8 + 72 - 1)^4 \\
 & := (-18 + 45 + 2 + 8 + 1 + 2 + 5)^5 & & := (1 - 8 + 7 + 38 + 8 + 72 - 1)^4 \\
 & := (18 - 4 + 5 + 28 + 1 + 2 - 5)^5 & & := (-1 + 8 + 7 + 38 - 8 + 72 + 1)^4 \\
 & := (18 - 4 - 5 + 28 + 1 + 2 + 5)^5 & & := (-1 - 8 + 7 + 38 + 8 + 72 + 1)^4
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 & := (-1 - 8 + 7 + 3 + 88 + 7 + 21)^4 \\
 & := (-1 + 8 + 7 + 3 - 8 + 87 + 21)^4 \\
 & := (-1 - 8 + 7 + 3 + 8 + 87 + 21)^4 \\
 & := (187 + 3 + 8 - 8 - 72 - 1)^4 \\
 & := (187 + 3 - 8 + 8 - 72 - 1)^4 \\
 & := (-18 + 7 + 38 + 87 + 2 + 1)^4 \\
 & := (187 + 38 - 87 - 21)^4 \\
 & := (-18 - 738 + 872 + 1)^4 \\
 \mathbf{188132517} & := (1 + 88 - 1 - 32 + 517)^3 \\
 & := (-1 + 88 + 1 - 32 + 517)^3 \\
 & := (-1 + 8 + 81 - 32 + 517)^3 \\
 & := (18 + 813 - 251 - 7)^3 \\
 & := (188 - 132 + 517)^3 \\
 \mathbf{190109375} & := (190 + 1 + 09 + 375)^3 \\
 & := (1 + 90 + 109 + 375)^3 \\
 \mathbf{191102976} & := (1 + 9 + 1 + 1 + 02 + 9 + 7 - 6)^6 \\
 & := (1 + 9 - 1 - 1 + 029 - 7 - 6)^6 \\
 & := (-1 + 9 + 1 - 1 + 029 - 7 - 6)^6 \\
 & := (-1 + 9 - 1 + 1 + 029 - 7 - 6)^6 \\
 & := (1 - 9 + 1 + 1 + 029 + 7 - 6)^6 \\
 & := (19 + 11 - 02 + 9 - 7 - 6)^6 \\
 & := (19 + 11 + 02 - 9 + 7 - 6)^6 \\
 & := (19 + 1 + 10 - 2 + 9 - 7 - 6)^6 \\
 & := (19 + 1 + 10 + 2 - 9 + 7 - 6)^6 \\
 & := (1 + 91 + 1 - 02 + 9 - 76)^6 \\
 & := (-1 + 91 - 1 + 02 + 9 - 76)^6 \\
 & := (19 - 11 + 029 - 7 - 6)^6 \\
 & := (19 - 1 - 10 + 29 - 7 - 6)^6 \\
 & := (-1 + 9 - 1 + 102 - 9 - 76)^6 \\
 & := (-1 - 9 - 1 + 102 + 9 - 76)^6 \\
 & := (19 + 110 - 2 - 97 - 6)^6 \\
 & := (19 + 110 - 29 - 76)^6 \\
 \mathbf{193100552} & := (19 - 3 + 10 + 0552)^3 \\
 \mathbf{193877776} & := (-1 + 93 - 8 + 7 + 7 + 7 + 7 + 6)^4 \\
 & := (1 + 9 + 3 + 8 + 77 + 7 + 7 + 6)^4 \\
 & := (1 + 9 + 3 + 8 + 7 + 77 + 7 + 6)^4 \\
 & := (1 + 9 + 3 + 8 + 7 + 7 + 77 + 6)^4 \\
 & := (1 + 9 + 3 + 8 + 7 + 7 + 7 + 76)^4 \\
 & := (19 - 3 + 87 + 7 + 7 + 7 - 6)^4 \\
 & := (193 + 8 - 77 + 7 - 7 - 6)^4 \\
 & := (193 + 8 - 77 - 7 + 7 - 6)^4 \\
 & := (193 + 8 + 7 - 77 - 7 - 6)^4 \\
 & := (193 + 8 - 7 - 77 + 7 - 6)^4 \\
 & := (193 + 8 + 7 - 7 - 77 - 6)^4 \\
 & := (193 + 8 - 7 + 7 - 77 - 6)^4 \\
 & := (193 + 8 + 7 - 7 - 7 - 76)^4 \\
 & := (193 + 8 - 7 + 7 - 7 - 76)^4 \\
 & := (-19 - 3 - 8 + 77 + 77 - 6)^4 \\
 & := (-1 + 9 - 38 + 77 + 77 - 6)^4 \\
 & := (1 + 9 - 38 + 77 - 7 + 76)^4 \\
 & := (1 + 9 - 38 - 7 + 77 + 76)^4 \\
 \mathbf{196122941} & := (-19 + 612 + 2 - 9 - 4 - 1)^3 \\
 & := (-19 + 612 + 29 - 41)^3 \\
 \mathbf{196140025} & := (1 - 9 + 6 + 14002 + 5)^2 \\
 \mathbf{197137368} & := (1 + 9 + 713 - 73 - 68)^3 \\
 \mathbf{199176704} & := (1 - 99 + 1 + 7 + 670 + 4)^3 \\
 & := (-1 + 9 - 91 - 7 + 670 + 4)^3 \\
 \mathbf{200533921} & := (-2 - 005 + 33 + 92 + 1)^4 \\
 \mathbf{203297472} & := (20 - 3 + 2 + 97 + 472)^3 \\
 \mathbf{204336469} & := (-2 - 043 - 3 + 646 - 9)^3 \\
 & := (-20 - 43 - 3 + 646 + 9)^3 \\
 \mathbf{205962976} & := (2 + 05 + 9 + 6 + 2 + 9 + 7 + 6)^5 \\
 & := (20 + 5 + 9 + 6 - 2 + 9 - 7 + 6)^5 \\
 & := (20 + 5 + 9 + 6 + 2 - 9 + 7 + 6)^5 \\
 & := (20 + 5 - 9 + 6 + 2 + 9 + 7 + 6)^5 \\
 & := (2 - 05 + 9 + 62 - 9 - 7 - 6)^5 \\
 & := (2 - 05 - 9 + 62 + 9 - 7 - 6)^5 \\
 & := (-2 + 05 - 9 + 62 - 9 - 7 + 6)^5 \\
 & := (-2 + 05 + 9 + 6 + 29 - 7 + 6)^5 \\
 & := (20 - 5 - 9 + 62 - 9 - 7 - 6)^5 \\
 & := (-20 + 5 + 9 + 62 - 9 - 7 + 6)^5 \\
 & := (-20 + 5 - 9 + 62 + 9 - 7 + 6)^5 \\
 & := (20 - 5 + 9 + 6 + 29 - 7 - 6)^5 \\
 & := (20 - 5 + 9 - 6 + 29 - 7 + 6)^5
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 & := (-2 - 059 + 6 - 2 + 97 + 6)^5 \\
 & := (20 - 5 + 96 + 2 + 9 - 76)^5 \\
 & := (2 - 05 + 96 + 29 - 76)^5 \\
 \mathbf{208527857} & := (-20 + 8 + 527 + 85 - 7)^3 \\
 \mathbf{209584584} & := (2 + 09 + 584 - 5 + 8 - 4)^3 \\
 & := (2 - 09 + 584 + 5 + 8 + 4)^3 \\
 & := (2 + 09 - 5 + 8 - 4 + 584)^3 \\
 & := (2 - 09 + 5 + 8 + 4 + 584)^3 \\
 & := (20 - 9 + 584 - 5 + 8 - 4)^3 \\
 & := (20 - 9 - 5 + 8 - 4 + 584)^3 \\
 \mathbf{212776173} & := (-2 + 1 - 2 - 7 - 7 + 617 - 3)^3 \\
 & := (-21 - 2 + 7 - 7 + 617 + 3)^3 \\
 & := (-21 - 2 - 7 + 7 + 617 + 3)^3 \\
 & := (2 + 1 - 27 + 7 + 617 - 3)^3 \\
 & := (-2 - 1 - 27 + 7 + 617 + 3)^3 \\
 \mathbf{213847192} & := (-2 - 1 + 38 + 471 + 92)^3 \\
 \mathbf{214358881} & := (-2 + 14 + 3 + 5 + 8 - 8 - 8 - 1)^8 \\
 & := (-2 + 14 + 3 + 5 - 8 + 8 - 8 - 1)^8 \\
 & := (-2 + 14 - 3 - 5 + 8 + 8 - 8 - 1)^8 \\
 & := (-2 + 14 + 3 + 5 - 8 - 8 + 8 - 1)^8 \\
 & := (-2 + 14 - 3 - 5 + 8 - 8 + 8 - 1)^8 \\
 & := (-2 + 14 - 3 - 5 - 8 + 8 + 8 - 1)^8 \\
 & := (2 + 14 - 3 + 5 + 8 - 8 - 8 + 1)^8 \\
 & := (2 + 14 - 3 + 5 - 8 + 8 - 8 + 1)^8 \\
 & := (2 + 14 - 3 + 5 - 8 - 8 + 8 + 1)^8 \\
 & := (2 - 14 + 3 - 5 + 8 + 8 + 8 + 1)^8 \\
 & := (-2 - 14 - 3 + 5 + 8 + 8 + 8 + 1)^8 \\
 & := (-2 - 1 + 4 + 35 - 8 - 8 - 8 - 1)^8 \\
 & := (2 + 1 - 4 + 35 - 8 - 8 - 8 + 1)^8 \\
 & := (-21 + 4 + 35 + 8 - 8 - 8 + 1)^8 \\
 & := (-21 + 4 + 35 - 8 + 8 - 8 + 1)^8 \\
 & := (-21 + 4 + 35 - 8 - 8 + 8 + 1)^8 \\
 & := (-2 + 143 + 5 - 8 - 8 - 8 - 1)^4 \\
 & := (2 + 14 + 3 + 5 + 88 + 8 + 1)^4 \\
 & := (2 + 14 + 3 + 5 + 8 + 88 + 1)^4 \\
 & := (2 + 14 + 3 + 5 + 8 + 8 + 81)^4 \\
 & := (-2 - 1 - 43 + 58 + 8 - 8 - 1)^8 \\
 & := (-2 - 1 - 43 + 58 - 8 + 8 - 1)^8 \\
 & := (2 + 1 + 43 + 58 + 8 + 8 + 1)^4 \\
 & := (2 + 1 + 4 + 35 + 88 - 8 - 1)^4 \\
 & := (2 - 1 + 4 + 35 + 88 - 8 + 1)^4 \\
 & := (2 + 1 + 4 + 35 - 8 + 88 - 1)^4 \\
 & := (2 - 1 + 4 + 35 - 8 + 88 + 1)^4 \\
 & := (2 - 1 + 4 + 35 + 8 - 8 + 81)^4 \\
 & := (2 - 1 + 4 + 35 - 8 + 8 + 81)^4 \\
 & := (2 + 1 - 4 - 3 - 58 - 8 + 81)^8 \\
 & := (-2 - 1 - 4 + 3 - 58 - 8 + 81)^8 \\
 & := (-2 - 1 - 4 - 3 + 58 - 8 + 81)^4 \\
 & := (214 - 3 + 5 - 88 - 8 + 1)^4 \\
 & := (214 - 3 + 5 - 8 - 88 + 1)^4 \\
 & := (21 + 43 + 58 + 8 - 8 - 1)^4 \\
 & := (21 + 43 + 58 - 8 + 8 - 1)^4 \\
 & := (-21 - 43 + 58 + 8 + 8 + 1)^8 \\
 & := (-21 + 4 - 3 - 58 + 88 + 1)^8 \\
 & := (-21 + 4 - 3 - 58 + 8 + 81)^8 \\
 & := (-2 + 14 - 3 - 5 + 88 - 81)^8 \\
 & := (2 + 14 - 3 + 5 - 88 + 81)^8 \\
 & := (-2 + 1 + 43 + 58 - 88 - 1)^8 \\
 & := (-2 - 1 + 43 + 58 - 88 + 1)^8 \\
 & := (-2 + 1 + 43 + 58 - 8 - 81)^8 \\
 & := (-21 + 4 + 35 - 88 + 81)^8 \\
 \mathbf{218167208} & := (2 + 1 - 81 + 672 + 08)^3 \\
 & := (2 - 1 + 816 - 7 - 208)^3 \\
 \mathbf{219256227} & := (21 + 9 + 2 + 562 + 2 + 7)^3 \\
 & := (2 + 1 + 9 + 2 + 562 + 27)^3 \\
 & := (21 - 9 + 2 + 562 + 27)^3 \\
 \mathbf{221533456} & := (22 - 1 + 53 - 3 + 45 + 6)^4 \\
 & := (2 + 2 + 153 - 34 + 5 - 6)^4 \\
 & := (-221 - 5 - 3 + 345 + 6)^4 \\
 & := (22 + 15 + 33 - 4 + 56)^4 \\
 & := (-22 + 1 + 53 + 34 + 56)^4 \\
 & := (2 - 215 + 334 - 5 + 6)^4 \\
 \mathbf{223648543} & := (2 + 2 + 3 + 648 - 5 - 43)^3 \\
 & := (2 - 2 - 3 + 648 + 5 - 43)^3 \\
 & := (-2 + 2 - 3 + 648 + 5 - 43)^3 \\
 \mathbf{225866529} & := (2 - 2 - 58 + 6 + 652 + 9)^3
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 & := (-2 + 2 - 58 + 6 + 652 + 9)^3 \\
 & := (22 + 58 + 6 - 6 + 529)^3 \\
 & := (22 + 58 - 6 + 6 + 529)^3 \\
 \mathbf{228886641} & := (22 + 88 + 8 + 6 - 6 + 4 + 1)^4 \\
 & := (22 + 88 + 8 - 6 + 6 + 4 + 1)^4 \\
 & := (22 + 8 + 88 + 6 - 6 + 4 + 1)^4 \\
 & := (22 + 8 + 88 - 6 + 6 + 4 + 1)^4 \\
 & := (22 + 8 + 8 + 86 - 6 + 4 + 1)^4 \\
 & := (-2 + 28 + 88 + 6 + 6 - 4 + 1)^4 \\
 & := (2 + 28 + 88 + 6 - 6 + 4 + 1)^4 \\
 & := (2 + 28 + 88 - 6 + 6 + 4 + 1)^4 \\
 & := (-2 + 28 + 8 + 86 + 6 - 4 + 1)^4 \\
 & := (2 + 28 + 8 + 86 - 6 + 4 + 1)^4 \\
 & := (228 - 88 - 6 - 6 - 4 - 1)^4 \\
 & := (228 - 8 - 86 - 6 - 4 - 1)^4 \\
 & := (2 - 28 + 88 + 66 - 4 - 1)^4 \\
 & := (-2 - 2 + 88 + 86 - 6 - 41)^4 \\
 \mathbf{229345007} & := (-2 - 2 + 9 + 3 - 4 + 50 - 07)^5 \\
 & := (2 - 2 - 9 + 3 - 4 + 50 + 07)^5 \\
 & := (-2 + 2 - 9 + 3 - 4 + 50 + 07)^5 \\
 \mathbf{230346397} & := (-2 - 30 + 3 - 4 + 639 + 7)^3 \\
 & := (-2 + 3 - 034 + 639 + 7)^3 \\
 \mathbf{232608375} & := (-23 - 2 + 608 + 37 - 5)^3 \\
 \mathbf{236421376} & := (2 + 36 + 4 + 2 + 1 + 3 + 76)^4 \\
 & := (2 + 3 - 6 - 4 - 2 + 137 - 6)^4 \\
 & := (-2 + 3 - 6 - 4 + 2 + 137 - 6)^4 \\
 & := (23 + 64 + 21 + 3 + 7 + 6)^4 \\
 & := (-23 + 6 - 4 + 2 + 137 + 6)^4 \\
 & := (23 + 6 + 4 + 2 + 13 + 76)^4 \\
 & := (2 + 36 + 42 + 1 + 37 + 6)^4 \\
 & := (-2 + 36 - 4 + 21 - 3 + 76)^4 \\
 & := (2 - 3 + 64 - 2 - 13 + 76)^4 \\
 & := (-2 - 3 + 64 + 2 - 13 + 76)^4 \\
 & := (2 - 3 - 6 + 42 + 13 + 76)^4 \\
 & := (-23 + 6 + 4 + 213 - 76)^4 \\
 \mathbf{237176659} & := (23 - 71 - 7 + 665 + 9)^3 \\
 & := (-2 + 37 + 1 - 76 + 659)^3 \\
 \mathbf{244015641} & := (-24 + 4 + 015641)^2 \\
 \mathbf{244140625} & := (2 - 4 - 4 + 14 - 06 - 2 + 5)^{12} \\
 & := (2 + 4 + 4 - 14 + 06 - 2 + 5)^{12} \\
 & := (2 + 4 - 4 + 14 + 06 - 2 + 5)^6 \\
 & := (2 - 4 + 4 + 14 + 06 - 2 + 5)^6 \\
 & := (-2 - 4 - 4 + 14 - 06 + 2 + 5)^{12} \\
 & := (2 + 4 + 4 + 14 - 06 + 2 + 5)^6 \\
 & := (-2 + 4 + 4 - 14 + 06 + 2 + 5)^{12} \\
 & := (-2 + 4 - 4 + 14 + 06 + 2 + 5)^6 \\
 & := (-2 - 4 + 4 + 14 + 06 + 2 + 5)^6 \\
 & := (24 - 4 - 14 + 06 - 2 - 5)^{12} \\
 & := (24 + 4 - 14 - 06 + 2 - 5)^{12} \\
 & := (24 - 4 + 14 - 06 + 2 - 5)^6 \\
 & := (-2 + 44 - 14 - 06 - 2 + 5)^6 \\
 & := (-2 + 4 - 4 + 140 - 6 - 2 - 5)^4 \\
 & := (-2 - 4 + 4 + 140 - 6 - 2 - 5)^4 \\
 & := (2 - 4 - 4 + 140 - 6 + 2 - 5)^4 \\
 & := (2 + 4 + 4 + 14 + 06 - 25)^{12} \\
 & := (-24 - 4 + 140 + 6 + 2 + 5)^4 \\
 & := (-24 - 4 - 14 + 062 + 5)^6 \\
 & := (24 - 4 - 14 - 06 + 25)^6 \\
 & := (-24 - 4 + 14 - 06 + 25)^{12} \\
 & := (-24 + 4 + 14 + 06 + 25)^6 \\
 & := (-2 - 44 + 14 + 062 - 5)^6 \\
 & := (-2 + 44 + 14 - 06 - 25)^6 \\
 & := (-2 + 44 + 140 - 62 + 5)^4 \\
 & := (-2 - 44 + 140 + 6 + 25)^4 \\
 \mathbf{245314376} & := (-24 + 531 + 43 + 76)^3 \\
 \mathbf{246491883} & := (2 - 4 + 649 - 1 - 8 - 8 - 3)^3 \\
 & := (-24 + 649 - 1 + 8 - 8 + 3)^3 \\
 & := (-24 + 649 - 1 - 8 + 8 + 3)^3 \\
 \mathbf{247673152} & := (-2 - 47 + 673 + 1 + 5 - 2)^3 \\
 & := (-24 - 76 + 731 - 5 + 2)^3 \\
 & := (2 - 47 - 6 + 731 - 52)^3 \\
 \mathbf{251239591} & := (25 + 1 + 2 + 3 + 9 + 591)^3 \\
 & := (2 + 5 + 1 + 23 + 9 + 591)^3 \\
 & := (25 + 1 + 23 - 9 + 591)^3 \\
 \mathbf{252047376} & := (-2 + 52 + 04 + 73 - 7 + 6)^4 \\
 & := (-2 + 52 - 04 + 7 - 3 + 76)^4
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 & := (-2 + 52 + 04 - 7 + 3 + 76)^4 \\
 & := (-25 - 2 + 04 + 73 + 76)^4 \\
 & := (-2 - 5 - 20 + 4 + 73 + 76)^4 \\
 & := (252 - 047 - 3 - 76)^4 \\
 \mathbf{252435968} & := (25 + 2 + 4 - 3 + 596 + 8)^3 \\
 & := (2 + 524 - 3 + 5 + 96 + 8)^3 \\
 & := (2 + 5 + 24 - 3 + 596 + 8)^3 \\
 & := (-2 + 5 - 2 + 43 + 596 - 8)^3 \\
 \mathbf{253636137} & := (-2 + 5 + 3 + 636 + 1 - 3 - 7)^3 \\
 & := (-2 + 5 - 3 + 636 + 1 + 3 - 7)^3 \\
 & := (2 - 5 + 3 + 636 + 1 + 3 - 7)^3 \\
 & := (2 - 5 - 3 + 636 - 1 - 3 + 7)^3 \\
 & := (2 + 5 + 3 + 6 - 3 + 613 + 7)^3 \\
 & := (2 + 5 - 3 + 6 + 3 + 613 + 7)^3 \\
 & := (25 - 3 - 6 - 3 + 613 + 7)^3 \\
 & := (2 + 536 - 3 + 61 + 37)^3 \\
 \mathbf{254803968} & := (-2 + 54 - 8 - 03 + 9 + 6 - 8)^5 \\
 & := (2 + 5 - 4 + 8 + 039 + 6 - 8)^5 \\
 & := (-2 + 5 - 4 + 8 + 039 - 6 + 8)^5 \\
 & := (2 + 5 - 4 - 8 + 039 + 6 + 8)^5 \\
 & := (-25 - 4 - 8 - 03 + 96 - 8)^5 \\
 & := (2 - 54 + 80 - 3 + 9 + 6 + 8)^5 \\
 & := (2 - 5 - 4 + 80 - 39 + 6 + 8)^5 \\
 & := (2 + 5 + 4 + 8 - 039 + 68)^5 \\
 & := (-25 + 48 + 039 - 6 - 8)^5 \\
 & := (25 + 48 - 039 + 6 + 8)^5 \\
 & := (25 - 4 + 80 - 39 - 6 - 8)^5 \\
 & := (25 - 4 - 80 + 3 + 96 + 8)^5 \\
 & := (-2 - 5 + 4 + 80 + 39 - 68)^5 \\
 & := (25 - 4 - 80 + 39 + 68)^5 \\
 \mathbf{257259456} & := (2 + 572 + 59 + 4 + 5 - 6)^3 \\
 & := (-2 + 572 + 59 - 4 + 5 + 6)^3 \\
 & := (-2 + 572 + 5 + 9 - 4 + 56)^3 \\
 & := (-2 + 57 - 2 + 594 - 5 - 6)^3 \\
 \mathbf{258474853} & := (-25 - 84 + 748 - 5 + 3)^3 \\
 & := (258 - 474 + 853)^3 \\
 \mathbf{259694072} & := (2 + 596 + 9 + 40 - 7 - 2)^3 \\
 & := (-2 + 596 + 9 + 40 - 7 + 2)^3
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 & := (2 + 596 - 9 + 40 + 7 + 2)^3 \\
 & := (-2 - 59 + 694 + 07 - 2)^3 \\
 & := (2 + 5 + 9 + 694 - 072)^3 \\
 & := (25 - 9 + 694 - 072)^3 \\
 \mathbf{260144641} & := (-2 - 6 + 0144 - 6 - 4 + 1)^4 \\
 & := (-26 + 0144 + 6 + 4 - 1)^4 \\
 & := (2 + 60 + 14 + 46 + 4 + 1)^4 \\
 & := (2 + 60 + 14 + 4 + 6 + 41)^4 \\
 & := (260 - 144 + 6 + 4 + 1)^4 \\
 & := (26 + 014 + 46 + 41)^4 \\
 \mathbf{260917119} & := (2 + 609 + 17 + 1 + 1 + 9)^3 \\
 & := (2 + 609 + 1 + 7 + 11 + 9)^3 \\
 & := (2 + 609 + 1 + 7 + 1 + 19)^3 \\
 & := (-260 + 917 + 1 - 19)^3 \\
 \mathbf{262144000} & := (26 + 214 + 400 + 0)^3 \\
 \mathbf{263374721} & := (263 + 374 + 7 - 2 - 1)^3 \\
 \mathbf{265847707} & := (2 + 658 + 4 - 7 - 7 - 07)^3 \\
 & := (-2 - 65 - 8 + 4 + 7 + 707)^3 \\
 & := (2 + 6 + 5 - 84 + 7 + 707)^3 \\
 & := (2 - 6 - 5 - 8 - 47 + 707)^3 \\
 \mathbf{267089984} & := (-267 + 0899 + 8 + 4)^3 \\
 \mathbf{268336125} & := (26 + 8 - 3 - 3 + 612 + 5)^3 \\
 & := (2 + 683 - 36 - 1 + 2 - 5)^3 \\
 \mathbf{268435456} & := (2 - 6 - 8 - 4 + 35 - 4 - 5 - 6)^{14} \\
 & := (2 + 6 - 8 - 4 + 35 - 4 - 5 - 6)^7 \\
 & := (-2 - 6 + 8 - 4 + 35 - 4 - 5 - 6)^7 \\
 & := (-2 - 6 - 8 + 4 + 35 + 4 - 5 - 6)^7 \\
 & := (2 - 6 - 8 - 4 + 35 - 4 - 5 + 6)^7 \\
 & := (-26 + 8 + 4 + 35 - 4 + 5 - 6)^7 \\
 & := (-26 + 8 - 4 + 35 + 4 + 5 - 6)^7 \\
 & := (-26 - 8 + 4 + 35 - 4 - 5 + 6)^{28} \\
 & := (-26 - 8 - 4 + 35 + 4 - 5 + 6)^{28} \\
 & := (26 + 8 - 4 - 35 - 4 + 5 + 6)^{28} \\
 & := (-26 - 8 - 4 + 35 - 4 + 5 + 6)^{14} \\
 & := (26 - 8 + 4 - 35 + 4 + 5 + 6)^{28} \\
 & := (-26 - 8 - 4 - 3 + 54 - 5 - 6)^{28} \\
 & := (-26 - 8 + 4 + 3 + 54 - 5 - 6)^7 \\
 & := (-26 - 8 - 4 - 3 + 5 - 4 + 56)^7
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 &:= (2 + 68 - 4 - 35 - 4 - 5 - 6)^7 & &:= (2 - 6 - 8 - 43 + 5 - 4 + 56)^{28} \\
 &:= (-2 + 68 + 4 - 3 - 54 - 5 - 6)^{28} & &:= (2 - 6 + 8 - 43 - 5 + 4 + 56)^7 \\
 &:= (2 + 68 - 4 + 3 - 54 - 5 - 6)^{14} & &:= (2 + 6 + 8 + 4 + 35 - 45 - 6)^{14} \\
 &:= (-2 + 68 - 4 - 3 - 54 + 5 - 6)^{14} & &:= (2 - 6 + 8 - 4 - 35 + 45 - 6)^{14} \\
 &:= (2 + 68 + 4 - 3 - 54 + 5 - 6)^7 & &:= (2 + 6 + 8 - 4 - 35 + 45 - 6)^7 \\
 &:= (2 + 68 - 4 + 3 - 54 - 5 + 6)^7 & &:= (-2 + 6 - 8 + 4 - 35 + 45 - 6)^{14} \\
 &:= (-2 + 68 + 4 + 3 + 54 - 5 + 6)^4 & &:= (-2 + 6 + 8 - 4 + 35 - 45 + 6)^{14} \\
 &:= (-2 + 68 - 4 - 3 - 54 + 5 + 6)^7 & &:= (2 - 6 + 8 + 4 + 35 - 45 + 6)^{14} \\
 &:= (2 + 68 - 4 - 3 + 54 + 5 + 6)^4 & &:= (2 + 6 + 8 + 4 + 35 - 45 + 6)^7 \\
 &:= (-2 - 68 + 4 + 3 + 54 + 5 + 6)^{28} & &:= (2 - 6 + 8 - 4 - 35 + 45 + 6)^7 \\
 &:= (-2 + 68 + 4 - 3 - 5 - 4 - 56)^{28} & &:= (-2 - 6 - 8 + 4 - 35 + 45 + 6)^{14} \\
 &:= (2 + 68 - 4 + 3 - 5 - 4 - 56)^{14} & &:= (-2 + 6 - 8 + 4 - 35 + 45 + 6)^7 \\
 &:= (-2 + 68 - 4 - 3 + 5 - 4 - 56)^{14} & &:= (-26 + 84 - 35 + 4 - 5 - 6)^7 \\
 &:= (2 + 68 + 4 - 3 + 5 - 4 - 56)^7 & &:= (-26 + 84 - 3 - 54 - 5 + 6)^{28} \\
 &:= (-2 + 68 - 4 - 3 - 5 + 4 - 56)^{28} & &:= (26 - 84 - 3 + 54 + 5 + 6)^{14} \\
 &:= (-2 + 68 + 4 + 3 - 5 + 4 - 56)^7 & &:= (-26 + 84 + 3 - 5 + 4 - 56)^{14} \\
 &:= (2 + 68 - 4 - 3 + 5 + 4 - 56)^7 & &:= (26 - 84 + 3 + 5 - 4 + 56)^{28} \\
 &:= (2 + 68 + 4 - 3 + 5 - 4 + 56)^4 & &:= (26 - 84 - 3 + 5 + 4 + 56)^{14} \\
 &:= (-2 + 68 + 4 + 3 - 5 + 4 + 56)^4 & &:= (-26 + 8 - 43 + 54 + 5 + 6)^{14} \\
 &:= (2 + 68 - 4 - 3 + 5 + 4 + 56)^4 & &:= (26 - 8 + 43 - 5 + 4 - 56)^{14} \\
 &:= (-2 - 68 + 4 + 3 + 5 + 4 + 56)^{28} & &:= (-26 + 8 - 43 + 5 + 4 + 56)^{14} \\
 &:= (-2 + 6 + 84 + 35 + 4 - 5 + 6)^4 & &:= (-26 + 8 + 4 - 35 + 45 + 6)^{28} \\
 &:= (-2 + 6 + 84 - 3 + 54 - 5 - 6)^4 & &:= (-2 - 68 + 43 + 54 - 5 - 6)^7 \\
 &:= (-2 - 6 + 84 - 3 + 54 - 5 + 6)^4 & &:= (2 - 68 - 4 + 35 + 45 - 6)^{14} \\
 &:= (-2 - 6 + 84 - 3 - 5 + 4 - 56)^7 & &:= (2 - 68 - 4 + 35 + 45 + 6)^7 \\
 &:= (-2 - 6 + 84 - 3 - 5 + 4 + 56)^4 & &:= (-2 + 6 + 84 - 35 - 45 - 6)^{28} \\
 &:= (2 - 6 + 8 - 43 + 54 - 5 - 6)^{14} & &:= (-2 - 6 + 84 - 35 - 45 + 6)^{28} \\
 &:= (2 + 6 + 8 - 43 + 54 - 5 - 6)^7 & &:= (26 - 84 + 35 + 45 - 6)^7 \\
 &:= (2 + 6 + 8 + 43 - 54 + 5 - 6)^{14} & &:= (-2 + 684 - 3 - 545 - 6)^4 \\
 &:= (-2 + 6 + 8 + 43 - 54 - 5 + 6)^{28} & &:= (-268 + 435 - 45 + 6)^4 \\
 &:= (2 - 6 + 8 - 43 + 54 - 5 + 6)^7 & & \mathbf{269586136} := (2 + 695 - 8 - 6 - 1 - 36)^3 \\
 &:= (2 - 6 + 8 + 43 - 54 + 5 + 6)^{14} & &:= (2 + 695 - 86 - 1 + 36)^3 \\
 &:= (2 + 6 + 8 + 43 - 54 + 5 + 6)^7 & &:= (-2 + 69 + 586 - 13 + 6)^3 \\
 &:= (2 + 6 + 8 + 43 + 5 - 4 - 56)^{14} & & \mathbf{270840023} := (2 + 708 - 40 - 023)^3 \\
 &:= (2 + 6 + 8 + 43 - 5 + 4 - 56)^{28} & & \mathbf{272097792} := (-27 - 20 - 97 + 792)^3 \\
 &:= (2 + 6 - 8 - 43 - 5 - 4 + 56)^{14} & & \mathbf{273359449} := (2 + 733 - 5 - 94 + 4 + 9)^3 \\
 &:= (-2 - 6 + 8 - 43 - 5 - 4 + 56)^{14} & &:= (-2 + 73 - 3 + 594 - 4 - 9)^3 \\
 &:= (-2 + 6 + 8 - 43 - 5 - 4 + 56)^7 & &:= (2 + 7 + 33 + 594 + 4 + 9)^3
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 & := (273 + 359 + 4 + 4 + 9)^3 & := (28 + 2 - 4 - 7 - 5 - 2 + 4 - 9)^{10} \\
 & := (27 + 33 + 594 + 4 - 9)^3 & := (28 - 2 - 4 - 7 - 5 + 2 + 4 - 9)^{10} \\
 & := (-27 + 33 + 594 + 49)^3 & := (28 + 2 + 4 + 7 + 5 - 2 - 4 + 9)^5 \\
 \mathbf{276922881} & := (27 + 6 + 9 + 2 - 2 + 88 - 1)^4 & := (28 - 2 + 4 + 7 + 5 + 2 - 4 + 9)^5 \\
 & := (27 + 6 + 9 - 2 + 2 + 88 - 1)^4 & := (28 + 2 - 4 + 7 + 5 - 2 + 4 + 9)^5 \\
 & := (-2 - 7 + 69 - 2 - 2 - 8 + 81)^4 & := (28 - 2 - 4 + 7 + 5 + 2 + 4 + 9)^5 \\
 & := (-2 + 7 + 6 + 9 + 22 + 88 - 1)^4 & := (-2 + 82 - 4 - 7 - 5 - 2 - 4 - 9)^5 \\
 & := (27 + 69 - 2 + 28 + 8 - 1)^4 & := (2 + 8 + 24 - 7 - 5 - 2 - 4 - 9)^{10} \\
 & := (-27 + 69 + 2 - 2 + 88 - 1)^4 & := (-2 + 8 + 24 - 7 - 5 + 2 - 4 - 9)^{10} \\
 & := (-27 + 69 - 2 + 2 + 88 - 1)^4 & := (2 + 8 + 24 + 7 + 5 - 2 - 4 + 9)^5 \\
 & := (-2 + 76 + 92 - 28 - 8 - 1)^4 & := (-2 + 8 + 24 + 7 + 5 + 2 - 4 + 9)^5 \\
 & := (2 - 7 + 69 - 22 + 88 - 1)^4 & := (2 + 8 + 2 + 47 + 5 - 2 - 4 - 9)^5 \\
 & := (2 + 7 + 69 - 22 - 8 + 81)^4 & := (2 + 8 - 2 + 47 + 5 + 2 - 4 - 9)^5 \\
 & := (2 + 7 + 69 - 2 - 28 + 81)^4 & := (-2 + 8 + 2 + 47 + 5 + 2 - 4 - 9)^5 \\
 & := (-2 + 7 + 69 + 2 - 28 + 81)^4 & := (-2 + 8 - 2 + 47 + 5 - 2 + 4 - 9)^5 \\
 \mathbf{282300416} & := (2 + 8 + 230 + 0416)^3 & := (-2 + 8 - 2 + 47 - 5 - 2 - 4 + 9)^5 \\
 \mathbf{282475249} & := (2 + 8 + 2 + 4 + 7 - 5 + 2 - 4 - 9)^{10} & := (2 - 8 + 2 + 47 - 5 - 2 + 4 + 9)^5 \\
 & := (2 + 8 - 2 + 4 + 7 - 5 - 2 + 4 - 9)^{10} & := (2 - 8 - 2 + 47 - 5 + 2 + 4 + 9)^5 \\
 & := (-2 + 8 + 2 + 4 + 7 - 5 - 2 + 4 - 9)^{10} & := (-2 - 8 + 2 + 47 - 5 + 2 + 4 + 9)^5 \\
 & := (2 + 8 + 2 + 4 - 7 + 5 - 2 + 4 - 9)^{10} & := (2 + 8 - 2 - 4 - 7 - 5 + 24 - 9)^{10} \\
 & := (2 + 8 + 2 - 4 + 7 - 5 + 2 + 4 - 9)^{10} & := (-2 + 8 + 2 - 4 - 7 - 5 + 24 - 9)^{10} \\
 & := (-2 + 8 - 2 + 4 + 7 - 5 + 2 + 4 - 9)^{10} & := (2 + 8 - 2 - 4 + 7 + 5 + 24 + 9)^5 \\
 & := (2 + 8 - 2 + 4 - 7 + 5 + 2 + 4 - 9)^{10} & := (-2 + 8 + 2 - 4 + 7 + 5 + 24 + 9)^5 \\
 & := (-2 + 8 + 2 + 4 - 7 + 5 + 2 + 4 - 9)^{10} & := (-2 + 8 - 2 - 4 + 7 - 5 - 2 + 49)^5 \\
 & := (2 + 8 + 2 + 4 - 7 - 5 - 2 - 4 + 9)^{10} & := (2 - 8 + 2 + 4 + 7 - 5 - 2 + 49)^5 \\
 & := (2 - 8 + 2 - 4 + 7 + 5 - 2 - 4 + 9)^{10} & := (2 + 8 - 2 - 4 - 7 + 5 - 2 + 49)^5 \\
 & := (-2 - 8 - 2 + 4 + 7 + 5 - 2 - 4 + 9)^{10} & := (-2 + 8 + 2 - 4 - 7 + 5 - 2 + 49)^5 \\
 & := (2 + 8 - 2 + 4 - 7 - 5 + 2 - 4 + 9)^{10} & := (2 - 8 - 2 + 4 + 7 - 5 + 2 + 49)^5 \\
 & := (-2 + 8 + 2 + 4 - 7 - 5 + 2 - 4 + 9)^{10} & := (-2 - 8 + 2 + 4 + 7 - 5 + 2 + 49)^5 \\
 & := (2 - 8 - 2 - 4 + 7 + 5 + 2 - 4 + 9)^{10} & := (-2 + 8 - 2 - 4 - 7 + 5 + 2 + 49)^5 \\
 & := (-2 - 8 + 2 - 4 + 7 + 5 + 2 - 4 + 9)^{10} & := (2 - 8 + 2 + 4 - 7 + 5 + 2 + 49)^5 \\
 & := (2 + 8 + 2 - 4 - 7 - 5 - 2 + 4 + 9)^{10} & := (28 + 24 + 7 + 5 - 2 - 4 - 9)^5 \\
 & := (-2 + 8 - 2 + 4 - 7 - 5 - 2 + 4 + 9)^{10} & := (28 - 24 - 7 - 5 + 2 + 4 + 9)^{10} \\
 & := (-2 - 8 - 2 - 4 + 7 + 5 - 2 + 4 + 9)^{10} & := (-28 - 2 + 47 + 5 - 2 - 4 - 9)^{10} \\
 & := (2 + 8 - 2 - 4 - 7 - 5 + 2 + 4 + 9)^{10} & := (28 - 2 - 4 + 7 + 5 + 24 - 9)^5 \\
 & := (-2 + 8 + 2 - 4 - 7 - 5 + 2 + 4 + 9)^{10} & := (28 + 2 + 4 - 7 - 5 - 24 + 9)^{10} \\
 & := (28 + 2 + 4 - 7 - 5 - 2 - 4 - 9)^{10} & := (2 + 82 - 47 + 5 + 2 - 4 + 9)^5 \\
 & := (28 - 2 + 4 - 7 - 5 + 2 - 4 - 9)^{10} & := (-2 + 82 - 47 + 5 - 2 + 4 + 9)^5
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} &:= (2 + 82 - 4 + 7 - 5 - 24 - 9)^5 \\ &:= (-2 + 82 + 4 - 7 + 5 - 24 - 9)^5 \\ &:= (-2 + 82 - 4 - 7 - 5 - 24 + 9)^5 \\ &:= (2 + 82 + 4 + 7 + 5 - 2 - 49)^5 \\ &:= (-2 + 82 + 4 + 7 + 5 + 2 - 49)^5 \\ &:= (2 + 8 + 24 - 7 - 5 - 24 + 9)^{10} \\ &:= (2 + 8 - 24 - 7 - 5 + 24 + 9)^{10} \\ &:= (-2 - 8 + 24 + 7 - 5 + 24 + 9)^5 \\ &:= (2 - 8 + 24 - 7 + 5 + 24 + 9)^5 \\ &:= (-2 - 8 + 24 - 7 - 5 - 2 + 49)^5 \\ &:= (2 + 8 - 24 + 7 + 5 + 2 + 49)^5 \\ &:= (-2 - 8 - 2 + 47 + 5 - 24 - 9)^{10} \\ &:= (2 - 8 - 2 + 47 - 5 + 24 - 9)^5 \\ &:= (-2 - 8 + 2 + 47 - 5 + 24 - 9)^5 \\ &:= (2 + 8 + 2 + 47 + 5 - 24 + 9)^5 \\ &:= (2 + 8 + 2 + 47 - 5 + 2 - 49)^{10} \\ &:= (2 + 8 + 2 - 47 - 5 - 2 + 49)^{10} \\ &:= (2 + 8 - 2 - 47 - 5 + 2 + 49)^{10} \\ &:= (-2 + 8 + 2 - 47 - 5 + 2 + 49)^{10} \\ &:= (28 + 24 - 7 - 5 - 24 - 9)^{10} \\ &:= (28 - 24 - 7 - 5 + 24 - 9)^{10} \\ &:= (28 + 24 + 7 + 5 - 24 + 9)^5 \\ &:= (28 - 24 + 7 + 5 + 24 + 9)^5 \\ &:= (28 + 24 + 7 - 5 + 2 - 49)^{10} \\ &:= (28 - 24 - 7 + 5 - 2 + 49)^5 \\ &:= (-28 - 24 + 7 + 5 - 2 + 49)^{10} \\ &:= (-28 + 24 + 7 - 5 + 2 + 49)^5 \\ &:= (28 + 2 + 47 + 5 - 24 - 9)^5 \\ &:= (-28 - 2 + 47 + 5 - 24 + 9)^{10} \\ &:= (28 - 2 - 47 - 5 + 24 + 9)^{10} \\ &:= (-28 + 2 + 47 - 5 + 24 + 9)^5 \\ &:= (282 + 4 + 7 + 5 - 249)^5 \\ &:= (2 + 8 - 247 - 5 + 249)^{10} \end{aligned}$$

$$\mathbf{283593393} := (-283 - 5 + 933 + 9 + 3)^3$$

$$\mathbf{286191179} := (-28 + 619 - 11 + 79)^3$$

$$\mathbf{288804781} := (-28 - 88 - 04 + 781)^3$$

$$:= (-28 - 8 - 80 - 4 + 781)^3$$

$$\mathbf{294499921} := (2 + 94 - 49 - 9 + 92 + 1)^4$$

$$\mathbf{295408296} := (29 + 540 + 82 + 9 + 6)^3$$

$$\mathbf{296740963} := (2 + 9 + 674 - 09 - 6 - 3)^3$$

$$:= (2 - 9 + 674 + 09 - 6 - 3)^3$$

$$:= (2 - 9 + 674 - 09 + 6 + 3)^3$$

$$:= (2 - 9 + 6 + 740 - 9 - 63)^3$$

$$\mathbf{298077632} := (-2 - 98 + 07 + 763 - 2)^3$$

$$:= (-29 - 80 + 776 + 3 - 2)^3$$

$$\mathbf{298287441} := (2 + 9828 + 7441)^2$$

$$\mathbf{299418309} := (29 + 941 + 8 - 309)^3$$

$$:= (2 + 994 - 18 - 309)^3$$

$$\mathbf{300814336} := (3008 + 14336)^2$$

$$\mathbf{302111711} := (-30 + 2 - 11 - 1 + 711)^3$$

$$:= (-30 + 2 - 1 - 11 + 711)^3$$

$$:= (-30 - 21 + 11 + 711)^3$$

$$\mathbf{303595776} := (30 + 35 + 9 + 57 + 7 - 6)^4$$

$$:= (30 + 35 - 9 + 5 + 77 - 6)^4$$

$$:= (-30 + 3 - 5 + 95 - 7 + 76)^4$$

$$:= (3 - 035 + 95 - 7 + 76)^4$$

$$:= (303 - 5 - 95 - 77 + 6)^4$$

$$\mathbf{306182024} := (30 + 618 + 20 + 2 + 4)^3$$

$$:= (30 + 618 + 2 + 024)^3$$

$$\mathbf{307546875} := (-3 + 0754 + 6 - 87 + 5)^3$$

$$:= (30 + 7 + 546 + 87 + 5)^3$$

$$:= (30 + 7 - 54 + 687 + 5)^3$$

$$\mathbf{308915776} := (-3 + 08 + 9 - 1 + 5 + 7 + 7 - 6)^6$$

$$:= (-3 + 08 + 9 + 1 + 5 + 7 - 7 + 6)^6$$

$$:= (-3 + 08 + 9 + 1 + 5 - 7 + 7 + 6)^6$$

$$:= (3 + 08 - 9 - 1 + 5 + 7 + 7 + 6)^6$$

$$:= (30 - 8 + 9 + 15 - 7 - 7 - 6)^6$$

$$:= (30 + 8 + 9 - 15 + 7 - 7 - 6)^6$$

$$:= (30 + 8 + 9 - 15 - 7 + 7 - 6)^6$$

$$:= (-30 + 8 - 9 - 1 + 57 + 7 - 6)^6$$

$$:= (-30 - 8 + 9 - 1 + 57 - 7 + 6)^6$$

$$:= (-30 + 8 - 9 + 1 + 57 - 7 + 6)^6$$

$$:= (-30 - 8 - 9 - 1 + 5 - 7 + 76)^6$$

$$:= (-3 + 08 + 91 - 57 - 7 - 6)^6$$

$$:= (3 + 08 + 91 - 5 - 77 + 6)^6$$

$$:= (3 + 089 + 1 + 577 + 6)^3$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 & := (-308 + 915 - 7 + 76)^3 \\
 \mathbf{311665752} & := (3 + 1 - 1 + 665 + 7 + 5 - 2)^3 \\
 & := (3 - 1 + 1 + 665 + 7 + 5 - 2)^3 \\
 & := (-3 + 1 + 1 + 665 + 7 + 5 + 2)^3 \\
 & := (31 - 1 - 6 + 657 - 5 + 2)^3 \\
 & := (-3 + 11 + 6 + 657 + 5 + 2)^3 \\
 & := (3 - 1 + 16 + 657 + 5 - 2)^3 \\
 & := (-3 + 1 + 16 + 657 + 5 + 2)^3 \\
 & := (-3 + 1 - 1 - 66 - 5 + 752)^3 \\
 & := (-3 - 1 + 1 - 66 - 5 + 752)^3 \\
 & := (-3 + 1 - 1 - 6 - 65 + 752)^3 \\
 & := (-3 - 1 + 1 - 6 - 65 + 752)^3 \\
 & := (-31 - 1 + 665 - 7 + 52)^3 \\
 \mathbf{312500000} & := (3 - 1 - 2 + 50 + 0000)^5 \\
 & := (-3 + 1 + 2 + 50 + 0000)^5 \\
 \mathbf{312900721} & := (31 + 2 + 90 + 07 + 2 + 1)^4 \\
 & := (31 + 29 + 0072 + 1)^4 \\
 & := (31 - 2 + 90 - 07 + 21)^4 \\
 & := (3 + 12 + 90 + 07 + 21)^4 \\
 & := (312 - 900 + 721)^4 \\
 \mathbf{313046839} & := (3 + 1 - 3 + 04 + 683 - 9)^3 \\
 & := (-3 + 1 + 3 + 04 + 683 - 9)^3 \\
 & := (31 - 30 + 4 + 683 - 9)^3 \\
 \mathbf{317214568} & := (3 + 1 + 721 - 45 - 6 + 8)^3 \\
 \mathbf{318611987} & := (3 - 1 - 8 + 611 - 9 + 87)^3 \\
 \mathbf{322417936} & := (3 + 22 + 4 - 1 + 7 + 93 + 6)^4 \\
 & := (3 + 2 + 24 - 1 + 7 + 93 + 6)^4 \\
 & := (3 - 2 - 2 + 41 + 7 + 93 - 6)^4 \\
 & := (-3 + 2 + 2 + 41 - 7 + 93 + 6)^4 \\
 & := (32 + 2 - 4 + 17 + 93 - 6)^4 \\
 & := (-3 + 224 + 1 - 79 - 3 - 6)^4 \\
 & := (3 + 224 - 1 + 7 - 93 - 6)^4 \\
 & := (3 + 224 + 1 - 7 - 93 + 6)^4 \\
 & := (-3 + 2 + 241 - 7 - 93 - 6)^4 \\
 \mathbf{324242703} & := (32 - 42 - 4 - 2 + 703)^3 \\
 & := (32 - 4 - 2 - 42 + 703)^3 \\
 \mathbf{325660672} & := (-3 + 2 + 5 + 6 + 6 + 0672)^3 \\
 & := (32 - 5 + 660 + 6 - 7 + 2)^3 \\
 & := (3 + 25 - 6 - 6 + 0672)^3 \\
 & := (-3 + 2 + 5 + 6 + 606 + 72)^3 \\
 & := (-32 - 5 + 660 + 67 - 2)^3 \\
 \mathbf{327082769} & := (3 + 2 + 708 - 2 - 7 - 6 - 9)^3 \\
 & := (3 - 2 + 708 + 2 - 7 - 6 - 9)^3 \\
 & := (3 + 2 + 708 - 27 - 6 + 9)^3 \\
 & := (-3 - 2 + 7 - 082 + 769)^3 \\
 & := (3 - 2 - 70 + 827 - 69)^3 \\
 \mathbf{330621489} & := (-3306 + 21489)^2 \\
 \mathbf{331373888} & := (-33 - 13 + 738 + 8 - 8)^3 \\
 & := (-33 - 13 + 738 - 8 + 8)^3 \\
 \mathbf{332150625} & := (3 - 3 - 2 + 150 - 6 - 2 - 5)^4 \\
 & := (-3 + 3 - 2 + 150 - 6 - 2 - 5)^4 \\
 & := (-3 + 32 - 1 + 50 + 62 - 5)^4 \\
 & := (3 + 3 - 2 + 150 + 6 - 25)^4 \\
 & := (33 + 21 + 50 + 6 + 25)^4 \\
 \mathbf{337153536} & := (3 - 3 + 7 + 153 + 536)^3 \\
 & := (-3 + 3 + 7 + 153 + 536)^3 \\
 \mathbf{338608873} & := (3 - 3 + 8 + 608 + 8 + 73)^3 \\
 & := (-3 + 3 + 8 + 608 + 8 + 73)^3 \\
 \mathbf{342102016} & := (-3 + 42 + 102 + 01 - 6)^4 \\
 & := (342 + 1 - 0201 - 6)^4 \\
 \mathbf{345025251} & := (3 + 45 + 02 + 5 + 2 - 5 - 1)^5 \\
 & := (-3 + 45 + 02 + 5 - 2 + 5 - 1)^5 \\
 & := (3 + 45 + 02 - 5 + 2 + 5 - 1)^5 \\
 & := (-3 + 45 - 02 + 5 + 2 + 5 - 1)^5 \\
 & := (3 + 4 - 5 + 025 + 25 - 1)^5 \\
 & := (34 + 50 - 25 - 2 - 5 - 1)^5 \\
 & := (34 + 50 - 2 - 5 - 25 - 1)^5 \\
 & := (3 + 45 + 02 + 52 - 51)^5 \\
 \mathbf{348913664} & := (3 + 48 - 9 + 1 - 3 + 664)^3 \\
 & := (-3 + 48 - 9 + 1 + 3 + 664)^3 \\
 \mathbf{351895816} & := (-3 - 5 + 1 - 8 - 95 + 816)^3 \\
 \mathbf{352275361} & := (3 + 5 - 2 - 2 + 75 - 3 + 61)^4 \\
 & := (-3 + 5 - 2 - 2 + 75 + 3 + 61)^4 \\
 & := (3 - 5 + 2 - 2 + 75 + 3 + 61)^4 \\
 & := (3 - 5 - 2 + 2 + 75 + 3 + 61)^4 \\
 & := (3 + 5 + 22 - 7 + 53 + 61)^4
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 &:= (3 - 5 - 2 + 27 + 53 + 61)^4 \\
 &:= (3 + 5 - 227 - 5 + 361)^4 \\
 &:= (3 - 5 - 227 + 5 + 361)^4 \\
 &:= (3 - 5227 + 5361)^4 \\
 \mathbf{360944128} &:= (-360 + 944 + 128)^3 \\
 \mathbf{361190025} &:= (3 + 6 - 1 + 19002 - 5)^2 \\
 &:= (3 - 6 + 1 + 19002 + 5)^2 \\
 \mathbf{362467097} &:= (-3 + 6 - 2 + 4 + 6 + 709 - 7)^3 \\
 &:= (3 + 6 - 2 - 4 - 6 + 709 + 7)^3 \\
 &:= (3 - 6 + 2 + 4 - 6 + 709 + 7)^3 \\
 &:= (3 - 6 - 2 - 4 + 6 + 709 + 7)^3 \\
 &:= (-3 + 624 + 6 + 70 + 9 + 7)^3 \\
 &:= (-3 + 6 + 24 + 670 + 9 + 7)^3 \\
 \mathbf{362673936} &:= (-3 + 62 + 6 + 73 + 9 - 3 - 6)^4 \\
 &:= (3 + 62 - 6 + 73 + 9 + 3 - 6)^4 \\
 &:= (3 + 62 + 6 + 73 - 9 - 3 + 6)^4 \\
 &:= (-3 + 62 - 6 + 73 + 9 - 3 + 6)^4 \\
 &:= (-3 + 62 + 6 + 73 - 9 + 3 + 6)^4 \\
 &:= (3 + 6 + 26 + 7 - 3 + 93 + 6)^4 \\
 &:= (-3 + 6 + 26 + 7 + 3 + 93 + 6)^4 \\
 \mathbf{362797056} &:= (36 - 27 - 9 + 7 + 05 - 6)^{11} \\
 &:= (-36 + 27 + 9 + 7 + 05 - 6)^{11} \\
 &:= (-3 - 62 + 79 - 7 + 05 - 6)^{11} \\
 &:= (-3 - 62 - 7 + 9 + 70 + 5 - 6)^{11} \\
 &:= (-3 + 62 + 7 + 9 - 70 - 5 + 6)^{11} \\
 &:= (3 - 62 - 7 - 9 + 70 + 5 + 6)^{11} \\
 &:= (3 - 62 + 7 + 9 - 7 + 056)^{11} \\
 &:= (3 - 62 - 7 + 9 + 7 + 056)^{11} \\
 &:= (3 - 62 + 79 - 70 + 56)^{11} \\
 \mathbf{363994344} &:= (-3 + 639 - 9 + 43 + 44)^3 \\
 &:= (-3639 + 9 + 4344)^3 \\
 \mathbf{365525875} &:= (3 + 655 - 25 + 87 - 5)^3 \\
 &:= (365 - 525 + 875)^3 \\
 \mathbf{367061696} &:= (3 + 6 + 706 + 16 - 9 - 6)^3 \\
 &:= (-3 - 6 + 706 + 16 + 9 - 6)^3 \\
 &:= (3 - 6 + 706 + 16 - 9 + 6)^3 \\
 &:= (3 - 6 + 7 + 0616 + 96)^3 \\
 \mathbf{368601813} &:= (-3 - 6 - 86 - 01 + 813)^3
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 \mathbf{370146232} &:= (-3 + 701 - 4 - 6 - 2 + 32)^3 \\
 \mathbf{371694959} &:= (3 + 716 + 9 - 4 + 9 - 5 - 9)^3 \\
 &:= (3 + 716 + 9 + 4 - 9 + 5 - 9)^3 \\
 &:= (3 + 716 - 9 + 4 + 9 + 5 - 9)^3 \\
 &:= (3 + 716 + 9 - 4 - 9 - 5 + 9)^3 \\
 &:= (3 + 716 - 9 - 4 + 9 - 5 + 9)^3 \\
 &:= (3 + 716 - 9 + 4 - 9 + 5 + 9)^3 \\
 &:= (37 + 1 + 694 - 9 + 5 - 9)^3 \\
 \mathbf{374805361} &:= (3 + 748 + 05 - 36 + 1)^3 \\
 \mathbf{376367048} &:= (37 + 6 - 3 + 670 + 4 + 8)^3 \\
 &:= (-3 + 7 + 636 + 70 + 4 + 8)^3 \\
 &:= (3 - 7 - 6 + 36 + 704 - 8)^3 \\
 &:= (37 + 63 + 670 - 48)^3 \\
 \mathbf{380204032} &:= (3 + 8 + 02 + 040 - 3 + 2)^5 \\
 &:= (-3 + 8 + 02 + 040 + 3 + 2)^5 \\
 &:= (-3 + 80 - 20 - 4 - 03 + 2)^5 \\
 &:= (-3 + 80 + 20 - 40 - 3 - 2)^5 \\
 \mathbf{381078125} &:= (-3 + 810 - 78 - 1 + 2 - 5)^3 \\
 \mathbf{382657176} &:= (3 + 82 - 6 + 571 + 76)^3 \\
 \mathbf{384160000} &:= (-3 + 84 - 1 + 60 + 000)^4 \\
 \mathbf{384240583} &:= (3 + 842 - 40 + 5 - 83)^3 \\
 &:= (384 - 240 + 583)^3 \\
 \mathbf{385828352} &:= (3 + 858 + 2 - 83 - 52)^3 \\
 &:= (3 + 8 + 582 + 83 + 52)^3 \\
 &:= (385 + 8 + 283 + 52)^3 \\
 \mathbf{387420489} &:= (3 + 8 + 7 + 4 + 2 - 04 - 8 - 9)^{18} \\
 &:= (3 + 8 + 7 - 4 + 2 + 04 - 8 - 9)^{18} \\
 &:= (-3 + 8 + 7 + 4 - 2 - 04 + 8 - 9)^9 \\
 &:= (3 - 8 + 7 + 4 + 2 - 04 + 8 - 9)^{18} \\
 &:= (-3 + 8 + 7 - 4 - 2 + 04 + 8 - 9)^9 \\
 &:= (-3 + 8 - 7 + 4 - 2 + 04 + 8 - 9)^{18} \\
 &:= (3 + 8 - 7 + 4 - 2 + 04 + 8 - 9)^9 \\
 &:= (3 - 8 + 7 - 4 + 2 + 04 + 8 - 9)^{18} \\
 &:= (3 + 8 + 7 + 4 + 2 + 04 + 8 - 9)^6 \\
 &:= (-3 + 8 + 7 - 4 - 2 - 04 - 8 + 9)^{18} \\
 &:= (3 + 8 + 7 - 4 - 2 - 04 - 8 + 9)^9 \\
 &:= (3 + 8 - 7 + 4 - 2 - 04 - 8 + 9)^{18} \\
 &:= (3 + 8 - 7 - 4 - 2 + 04 - 8 + 9)^{18}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 & := (-3 - 8 + 7 + 4 - 2 + 04 - 8 + 9)^{18} & := (3 - 87 - 4 - 2 + 04 + 89)^{18} \\
 & := (3 - 8 + 7 + 4 - 2 + 04 - 8 + 9)^9 & := (-3 - 87 + 4 + 2 + 04 + 89)^9 \\
 & := (-3 + 8 - 7 + 4 + 2 + 04 - 8 + 9)^9 & := (3 + 8 + 7 + 42 - 048 - 9)^{18} \\
 & := (-3 - 8 + 7 - 4 - 2 - 04 + 8 + 9)^{18} & := (-3 + 8 + 7 - 42 + 048 - 9)^9 \\
 & := (3 - 8 + 7 - 4 - 2 - 04 + 8 + 9)^9 & := (3 - 8 - 7 - 42 + 048 + 9)^{18} \\
 & := (3 - 8 - 7 + 4 - 2 - 04 + 8 + 9)^{18} & := (-3 + 8 + 7 - 42 + 048 + 9)^6 \\
 & := (-3 + 8 + 7 + 4 - 2 - 04 + 8 + 9)^6 & := (3 - 8 - 7 - 4 - 20 + 48 - 9)^{18} \\
 & := (-3 + 8 - 7 - 4 + 2 - 04 + 8 + 9)^9 & := (-3 + 8 + 7 - 4 - 20 + 48 - 9)^6 \\
 & := (3 - 8 - 7 - 4 - 2 + 04 + 8 + 9)^{18} & := (3 + 8 - 7 + 4 - 20 + 48 - 9)^6 \\
 & := (-3 + 8 + 7 - 4 - 2 + 04 + 8 + 9)^6 & := (3 + 8 + 7 + 4 + 20 - 48 + 9)^{18} \\
 & := (3 + 8 - 7 + 4 - 2 + 04 + 8 + 9)^6 & := (-38 + 74 - 20 + 4 - 8 - 9)^{18} \\
 & := (-3 - 8 - 7 + 4 + 2 + 04 + 8 + 9)^9 & := (-3 + 87 - 42 - 048 + 9)^{18} \\
 & := (-3 - 8 - 7 + 42 - 04 - 8 - 9)^{18} & := (3 + 87 - 42 - 048 + 9)^9 \\
 & := (3 - 8 - 7 + 42 - 04 - 8 - 9)^9 & := (-3 - 87 + 42 + 048 + 9)^9 \\
 & := (-3 + 8 - 7 + 42 + 04 - 8 - 9)^6 & := (-3 + 87 - 4 - 20 - 48 - 9)^{18} \\
 & := (-3 - 8 - 7 + 42 + 04 + 8 - 9)^6 & := (3 + 87 - 4 - 20 - 48 - 9)^9 \\
 & := (3 - 8 - 7 + 42 - 04 - 8 + 9)^6 & := (3 + 87 - 4 - 20 - 48 + 9)^6 \\
 & := (-3 + 8 - 7 + 4 + 20 + 4 - 8 - 9)^9 & := (-3 - 87 + 4 + 20 + 4 + 89)^6 \\
 & := (-3 + 8 - 7 - 4 + 20 - 4 + 8 - 9)^9 & := (3 - 87 - 4 + 204 - 89)^6 \\
 & := (-3 - 8 - 7 + 4 + 20 + 4 + 8 - 9)^9 & := (-38 - 74 + 204 - 89)^{18} \\
 & := (-3 - 8 + 7 - 4 + 20 - 4 - 8 + 9)^9 & \mathbf{389017000} := (38 - 9 + 01 + 700 + 0)^3 \\
 & := (-3 - 8 - 7 + 4 + 20 - 4 - 8 + 9)^{18} & \mathbf{393832837} := (3 - 9 - 3 + 832 - 83 - 7)^3 \\
 & := (3 - 8 - 7 + 4 + 20 - 4 - 8 + 9)^9 & := (-3 - 9 + 3 + 832 - 83 - 7)^3 \\
 & := (-3 - 8 - 7 - 4 + 20 + 4 - 8 + 9)^{18} & := (393 + 8 + 328 - 3 + 7)^3 \\
 & := (3 - 8 - 7 - 4 + 20 + 4 - 8 + 9)^9 & \mathbf{395254161} := (3 + 95 + 2 - 5 + 41 + 6 - 1)^4 \\
 & := (-3 + 8 - 7 + 4 + 20 + 4 - 8 + 9)^6 & := (-3 + 95 - 2 + 5 + 41 + 6 - 1)^4 \\
 & := (-3 + 8 + 7 + 4 - 20 - 4 + 8 + 9)^9 & := (3 + 95 + 2 + 5 + 41 - 6 + 1)^4 \\
 & := (-3 + 8 - 7 - 4 + 20 - 4 + 8 + 9)^6 & := (-3 + 95 - 2 - 5 - 4 - 1 + 61)^4 \\
 & := (-3 + 8 + 7 - 4 - 20 + 4 + 8 + 9)^9 & := (-3 - 9 - 5 - 2 - 5 + 4 + 161)^4 \\
 & := (-3 + 8 - 7 + 4 - 20 + 4 + 8 + 9)^{18} & := (39 + 52 + 54 + 1 - 6 + 1)^4 \\
 & := (3 + 8 - 7 + 4 - 20 + 4 + 8 + 9)^9 & := (-3 + 9 - 5 - 25 + 4 + 161)^4 \\
 & := (-3 - 8 - 7 + 4 + 20 + 4 + 8 + 9)^6 & := (-395 + 2 + 541 - 6 - 1)^4 \\
 & := (-3 - 8 - 7 + 4 + 2 + 048 - 9)^6 & := (-3 - 95 + 254 - 16 + 1)^4 \\
 & := (3 + 87 - 42 - 04 - 8 - 9)^6 & \mathbf{395446904} := (-3 + 95 - 44 + 690 - 4)^3 \\
 & := (3 + 87 - 4 - 2 - 048 - 9)^6 & \mathbf{397065375} := (39 + 706 + 5 - 3 - 7 - 5)^3 \\
 & := (3 + 87 + 4 + 2 - 04 - 89)^{18} & := (39 + 706 - 5 - 3 - 7 + 5)^3 \\
 & := (3 + 87 - 4 + 2 + 04 - 89)^{18} & := (-3 + 97 + 0653 - 7 - 5)^3 \\
 & := (3 - 87 + 4 - 2 - 04 + 89)^{18} & := (-3 - 9 + 706 + 53 - 7 - 5)^3
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 \mathbf{398688256} &:= (39 + 8 + 688 + 2 + 5 - 6)^3 & &:= (-4 - 1 + 1 + 830 - 78 - 4)^3 \\
 &:= (-39 + 868 - 82 - 5 - 6)^3 & &:= (-4 + 1 + 1 - 8 - 30 + 784)^3 \\
 &:= (-3 + 9 + 868 - 82 - 56)^3 & & \mathbf{416832723} := (4 + 1 + 6 + 8 + 3 + 2 + 723)^3 \\
 &:= (398 - 6 + 88 + 256)^3 & & &:= (-4 + 1 + 683 - 2 + 72 - 3)^3 \\
 \mathbf{399920004} &:= (3 + 9 - 9 - 9 + 20004)^2 & & \mathbf{418161601} := (-4 + 1 - 8 + 161 - 6 - 01)^4 \\
 &:= (3 - 9 + 9 - 9 + 20004)^2 & & &:= (-4 - 1 - 8 + 161 - 6 + 01)^4 \\
 &:= (3 - 9 - 9 + 9 + 20004)^2 & & &:= (-4 + 1 - 8 + 1 - 6 + 160 - 1)^4 \\
 \mathbf{406586896} &:= (40 + 65 + 8 + 6 + 8 + 9 + 6)^4 & & &:= (-4 + 1 - 8 - 1 - 6 + 160 + 1)^4 \\
 &:= (40 + 6 + 5 + 86 + 8 - 9 + 6)^4 & & &:= (-4 - 1 - 8 + 1 - 6 + 160 + 1)^4 \\
 &:= (40 + 6 + 5 + 8 + 68 + 9 + 6)^4 & & &:= (41 + 81 + 6 + 16 - 01)^4 \\
 &:= (-4 + 065 + 86 - 8 + 9 - 6)^4 & & &:= (4 + 18 + 1 + 61 + 60 - 1)^4 \\
 &:= (4 + 065 + 8 + 68 - 9 + 6)^4 & & &:= (4 + 18 - 1 + 61 + 60 + 1)^4 \\
 &:= (-4 + 065 - 8 + 6 + 89 - 6)^4 & & & \mathbf{418195493} := (4 + 18 + 1 + 9 + 5 + 4 + 9 + 3)^5 \\
 &:= (-4 + 065 - 8 - 6 + 89 + 6)^4 & & & &:= (4 + 1 + 8 + 19 + 5 + 4 + 9 + 3)^5 \\
 &:= (-4 + 06 + 58 - 6 - 8 + 96)^4 & & & &:= (-4 - 1 + 8 - 1 + 9 + 54 - 9 - 3)^5 \\
 &:= (-4 - 06 + 58 + 6 - 8 + 96)^4 & & & &:= (-4 - 1 + 8 - 1 - 9 + 54 + 9 - 3)^5 \\
 &:= (-40 + 6 - 5 + 86 + 89 + 6)^4 & & & &:= (4 + 1 + 8 + 1 - 9 + 54 - 9 + 3)^5 \\
 \mathbf{406869021} &:= (40 + 6 + 8 + 690 - 2 - 1)^3 & & & &:= (4 + 1 - 8 - 1 + 9 + 54 - 9 + 3)^5 \\
 &:= (4 + 068 + 690 - 21)^3 & & & &:= (4 - 1 - 8 + 1 + 9 + 54 - 9 + 3)^5 \\
 \mathbf{410338673} &:= (4 + 1 + 03 + 3 + 8 - 6 + 7 - 3)^7 & & & &:= (4 + 1 - 8 - 1 - 9 + 54 + 9 + 3)^5 \\
 &:= (4 + 1 - 03 - 3 + 8 + 6 + 7 - 3)^7 & & & &:= (4 - 1 - 8 + 1 - 9 + 54 + 9 + 3)^5 \\
 &:= (4 + 1 + 03 - 3 + 8 - 6 + 7 + 3)^7 & & & &:= (41 + 8 + 19 - 5 - 4 - 9 + 3)^5 \\
 &:= (4 + 1 - 03 + 3 + 8 - 6 + 7 + 3)^7 & & & &:= (-41 + 8 - 1 + 95 + 4 - 9 - 3)^5 \\
 &:= (4 - 1 + 03 + 3 - 8 + 6 + 7 + 3)^7 & & & &:= (-41 + 8 + 1 + 95 - 4 - 9 + 3)^5 \\
 &:= (41 + 03 - 3 - 8 - 6 - 7 - 3)^7 & & & &:= (-41 - 8 - 1 + 95 - 4 + 9 + 3)^5 \\
 &:= (41 - 03 + 3 - 8 - 6 - 7 - 3)^7 & & & &:= (-41 + 8 + 1 - 9 + 5 - 4 + 93)^5 \\
 &:= (41 - 03 - 3 - 8 - 6 - 7 + 3)^7 & & & &:= (-41 - 8 - 1 + 9 + 5 - 4 + 93)^5 \\
 &:= (4 - 10 + 33 - 8 - 6 + 7 - 3)^7 & & & &:= (-41 - 8 + 1 + 9 - 5 + 4 + 93)^5 \\
 &:= (-4 - 10 + 33 + 8 - 6 - 7 + 3)^7 & & & &:= (4 + 18 - 1 - 9 - 5 + 49 - 3)^5 \\
 &:= (-4 - 10 - 3 + 38 + 6 - 7 - 3)^7 & & & &:= (-4 + 18 + 1 - 9 - 5 + 49 + 3)^5 \\
 &:= (-4 - 10 + 3 + 38 - 6 - 7 + 3)^7 & & & &:= (4 - 18 + 1 + 9 + 5 + 49 + 3)^5 \\
 &:= (4 + 103 - 3 - 8 - 6 - 73)^7 & & & &:= (4 + 1 + 81 + 9 - 54 + 9 + 3)^5 \\
 &:= (4 - 10 - 33 - 8 + 67 - 3)^7 & & & &:= (-4 - 1 - 8 + 19 - 5 + 49 + 3)^5 \\
 &:= (4 - 10 - 3 - 38 + 67 - 3)^7 & & & &:= (4 - 1 + 8 - 1 + 95 - 49 - 3)^5 \\
 &:= (-4 + 1 + 033 - 86 + 73)^7 & & & &:= (-4 + 1 + 8 - 1 + 95 - 49 + 3)^5 \\
 &:= (410 + 3 - 386 - 7 - 3)^7 & & & &:= (-4 - 1 + 8 + 1 + 95 - 49 + 3)^5 \\
 &:= (410 - 3 - 386 - 7 + 3)^7 & & & &:= (41 - 81 + 95 + 4 - 9 + 3)^5 \\
 \mathbf{411830784} &:= (-4 + 1 - 1 + 830 - 78 - 4)^3 & & & &:= (41 + 81 - 9 - 54 - 9 + 3)^5
 \end{aligned}$$

$:= (41 - 81 + 9 - 5 - 4 + 93)^5$	$:= (42 + 9 - 9 - 8 - 1 - 6 - 9 - 6)^8$
$:= (41 - 81 - 9 + 5 + 4 + 93)^5$	$:= (42 - 9 + 9 - 8 - 1 - 6 - 9 - 6)^8$
$:= (4 - 18 + 19 + 54 - 9 + 3)^5$	$:= (42 - 9 - 9 + 8 + 1 - 6 - 9 - 6)^8$
$:= (-4 - 18 - 19 + 5 - 4 + 93)^5$	$:= (42 - 9 - 9 - 8 - 1 - 6 + 9 - 6)^8$
$:= (4 + 18 + 1 - 9 - 54 + 93)^5$	$:= (4 + 29 + 9 - 8 - 1 - 6 - 9 - 6)^8$
$:= (4 - 1 - 8 + 19 - 54 + 93)^5$	$:= (4 + 29 - 9 + 8 + 1 - 6 - 9 - 6)^8$
$:= (41 - 8 - 19 - 54 + 93)^5$	$:= (4 + 29 - 9 - 8 - 1 - 6 + 9 - 6)^8$
418508992 $:= (4 - 1 + 850 - 8 - 99 + 2)^3$	$:= (-4 + 29 - 9 - 8 + 1 + 6 - 9 + 6)^8$
420189749 $:= (4 - 2 - 01 + 8 - 9 + 749)^3$	$:= (4 - 29 + 9 + 8 - 1 + 6 + 9 + 6)^8$
$:= (-4 + 2 + 01 - 8 + 9 + 749)^3$	$:= (-42 - 9 - 9 + 81 + 6 - 9 - 6)^8$
$:= (-4 + 20 + 1 - 8 - 9 + 749)^3$	$:= (-42 - 9 - 9 + 81 - 6 - 9 + 6)^8$
$:= (4 - 20 - 1 + 8 + 9 + 749)^3$	$:= (42 + 9 + 9 + 81 + 6 - 9 + 6)^4$
$:= (4 - 201 + 897 + 49)^3$	$:= (42 + 9 - 9 + 81 + 6 + 9 + 6)^4$
422055936 $:= (-4 - 2 + 20559 - 3 - 6)^2$	$:= (42 - 9 + 9 + 81 + 6 + 9 + 6)^4$
423564751 $:= (4 - 2 + 3 + 5 - 6 - 4 + 751)^3$	$:= (-42 + 9 - 9 - 8 - 1 + 69 - 6)^8$
$:= (4 + 2 - 3 - 5 + 6 - 4 + 751)^3$	$:= (-42 - 9 + 9 - 8 - 1 + 69 - 6)^8$
$:= (-4 - 2 + 3 + 5 - 6 + 4 + 751)^3$	$:= (-42 - 9 - 9 + 8 + 1 + 69 - 6)^8$
$:= (-4 + 2 - 3 - 5 + 6 + 4 + 751)^3$	$:= (42 + 9 + 9 + 8 + 1 + 69 + 6)^4$
428661064 $:= (-4 + 2 + 866 - 106 - 4)^3$	$:= (4 + 29 + 9 + 81 + 6 + 9 + 6)^4$
$:= (-4 - 2 + 86 + 610 + 64)^3$	$:= (-4 - 29 - 9 - 8 - 1 + 69 - 6)^8$
429981696 $:= (4 + 2 + 9 + 9 + 8 + 1 - 6 - 9 - 6)^8$	$:= (4 + 2 + 99 + 8 + 16 + 9 + 6)^4$
$:= (-4 - 2 + 9 + 9 + 8 + 1 + 6 - 9 - 6)^8$	$:= (4 + 2 + 99 + 8 + 1 - 6 - 96)^8$
$:= (4 + 2 + 9 + 9 - 8 - 1 - 6 + 9 - 6)^8$	$:= (-4 - 2 + 99 + 8 + 1 + 6 - 96)^8$
$:= (4 + 2 + 9 - 9 + 8 + 1 - 6 + 9 - 6)^8$	$:= (4 - 2 - 99 + 8 - 1 + 6 + 96)^8$
$:= (4 + 2 - 9 + 9 + 8 + 1 - 6 + 9 - 6)^8$	$:= (4 + 2 + 9 + 98 + 16 + 9 + 6)^4$
$:= (-4 - 2 + 9 + 9 - 8 - 1 + 6 + 9 - 6)^8$	$:= (4 + 2 + 9 + 98 + 1 - 6 - 96)^8$
$:= (-4 - 2 + 9 - 9 + 8 + 1 + 6 + 9 - 6)^8$	$:= (-4 - 2 + 9 + 98 + 1 + 6 - 96)^8$
$:= (-4 - 2 - 9 + 9 + 8 + 1 + 6 + 9 - 6)^8$	$:= (-4 + 2 + 9 - 98 + 1 + 6 + 96)^8$
$:= (-4 - 2 + 9 + 9 + 8 + 1 - 6 - 9 + 6)^8$	$:= (4 + 2 + 9 - 9 + 81 - 69 - 6)^8$
$:= (4 - 2 + 9 - 9 + 8 - 1 + 6 - 9 + 6)^8$	$:= (4 + 2 - 9 + 9 + 81 - 69 - 6)^8$
$:= (4 - 2 - 9 + 9 + 8 - 1 + 6 - 9 + 6)^8$	$:= (-4 - 2 + 9 - 9 + 81 - 69 + 6)^8$
$:= (-4 + 2 + 9 + 9 - 8 + 1 + 6 - 9 + 6)^8$	$:= (-4 - 2 - 9 + 9 + 81 - 69 + 6)^8$
$:= (-4 - 2 + 9 + 9 - 8 - 1 - 6 + 9 + 6)^8$	$:= (4 + 2 - 9 - 9 + 81 + 69 + 6)^4$
$:= (-4 - 2 + 9 - 9 + 8 + 1 - 6 + 9 + 6)^8$	$:= (4 + 2 + 9 + 9 + 8 + 16 + 96)^4$
$:= (-4 - 2 - 9 + 9 + 8 + 1 - 6 + 9 + 6)^8$	$:= (42 - 9 + 98 + 16 - 9 + 6)^4$
$:= (4 - 2 - 9 - 9 + 8 - 1 + 6 + 9 + 6)^8$	$:= (-42 - 9 - 9 - 8 - 16 + 96)^8$
$:= (-4 + 2 + 9 - 9 - 8 + 1 + 6 + 9 + 6)^8$	$:= (42 - 9 - 9 + 8 + 16 + 96)^4$
$:= (-4 + 2 - 9 + 9 - 8 + 1 + 6 + 9 + 6)^8$	$:= (4 + 29 + 98 + 16 - 9 + 6)^4$

$$\begin{aligned}
 &:= (4 + 29 - 9 + 8 + 16 + 96)^4 \\
 &:= (429 - 981 + 696)^4 \\
 \mathbf{432081216} &:= (-43 - 20 + 812 + 1 + 6)^3 \\
 \mathbf{433798093} &:= (4 - 33 + 798 - 09 - 3)^3 \\
 \mathbf{437245479} &:= (-43 + 724 - 5 + 4 + 79)^3 \\
 \mathbf{437520889} &:= (-4 + 37 - 5 + 20889)^2 \\
 \mathbf{438976000} &:= (4 - 3 + 8 - 9 + 760 + 00)^3 \\
 &:= (-4 + 3 - 8 + 9 + 760 + 00)^3 \\
 \mathbf{442050625} &:= (-4 + 42 + 050 + 62 - 5)^4 \\
 &:= (4 + 4 + 20 + 50 + 62 + 5)^4 \\
 &:= (44 + 20 + 50 + 6 + 25)^4 \\
 \mathbf{442450728} &:= (4 + 4 - 24 + 50 + 728)^3 \\
 \mathbf{447697125} &:= (44 + 7 + 6 - 9 + 712 + 5)^3 \\
 &:= (-4 + 47 + 6 + 9 + 712 - 5)^3 \\
 &:= (4 + 47 + 6 - 9 + 712 + 5)^3 \\
 &:= (44 + 7 + 697 + 12 + 5)^3 \\
 &:= (4 + 47 + 697 + 12 + 5)^3 \\
 \mathbf{451217663} &:= (-4 - 5 + 12 + 1 + 766 - 3)^3 \\
 &:= (4 + 5 - 12 + 1 + 766 + 3)^3 \\
 \mathbf{452984832} &:= (-45 + 2 - 9 - 8 - 4 + 832)^3 \\
 &:= (4 + 5 + 2 + 9 - 84 + 832)^3 \\
 &:= (-4 - 5 + 29 - 84 + 832)^3 \\
 \mathbf{454371856} &:= (4 + 54 + 3 + 7 - 1 + 85 - 6)^4 \\
 &:= (4 + 54 + 3 - 7 + 1 + 85 + 6)^4 \\
 &:= (-4 + 54 - 3 + 7 + 1 + 85 + 6)^4 \\
 &:= (-4 - 5 - 4 - 3 + 71 + 85 + 6)^4 \\
 &:= (45 + 43 - 7 + 1 + 8 + 56)^4 \\
 &:= (-45 + 4 + 3 - 7 + 185 + 6)^4 \\
 &:= (-45 - 4 - 3 + 7 + 185 + 6)^4 \\
 &:= (-4 - 5 - 43 + 7 + 185 + 6)^4 \\
 \mathbf{458314011} &:= (-45 + 831 - 4 - 011)^3 \\
 &:= (-4 - 5 + 831 - 40 - 11)^3 \\
 \mathbf{459165024} &:= (45 + 9 + 1 + 6 - 5 + 02 - 4)^5 \\
 &:= (45 + 9 - 1 - 6 + 5 - 02 + 4)^5 \\
 &:= (45 - 9 + 1 + 6 + 5 + 02 + 4)^5 \\
 &:= (-4 + 5 - 9 - 1 + 65 + 02 - 4)^5 \\
 &:= (4 - 5 - 9 + 1 + 65 + 02 - 4)^5 \\
 &:= (-4 - 5 - 9 + 1 + 65 + 02 + 4)^5 \\
 &:= (4 + 5 + 9 + 1 + 6 + 5 + 024)^5 \\
 &:= (4 + 59 - 16 + 5 - 02 + 4)^5 \\
 &:= (4 + 5 + 91 + 6 - 50 + 2 - 4)^5 \\
 &:= (-4 + 5 + 91 + 6 - 50 + 2 + 4)^5 \\
 &:= (4 - 5 - 9 + 16 + 50 + 2 - 4)^5 \\
 &:= (4 + 5 + 9 - 16 + 50 - 2 + 4)^5 \\
 &:= (-4 - 5 - 9 + 16 + 50 + 2 + 4)^5 \\
 &:= (-45 + 9 + 1 + 65 + 024)^5 \\
 &:= (-459 + 1 + 6 + 502 + 4)^5 \\
 &:= (-45 + 9 + 16 + 50 + 24)^5 \\
 \mathbf{461889917} &:= (-46 - 1 - 88 - 9 + 917)^3 \\
 &:= (-46 - 1 - 8 - 89 + 917)^3 \\
 &:= (-4 - 61 - 88 + 9 + 917)^3 \\
 \mathbf{463684824} &:= (4 - 6 - 36 - 8 - 4 + 824)^3 \\
 &:= (-4 - 6 - 36 - 8 + 4 + 824)^3 \\
 &:= (4 - 6 + 36 - 84 + 824)^3 \\
 \mathbf{465484375} &:= (4 - 6 - 54 + 843 - 7 - 5)^3 \\
 &:= (4 - 6 + 5 + 4 + 843 - 75)^3 \\
 \mathbf{466948881} &:= (-4 + 66 + 94 + 8 - 8 - 8 - 1)^4 \\
 &:= (-4 + 66 + 94 - 8 + 8 - 8 - 1)^4 \\
 &:= (-4 + 66 + 94 - 8 - 8 + 8 - 1)^4 \\
 &:= (-46 - 694 + 888 - 1)^4 \\
 \mathbf{467288576} &:= (46 + 728 + 8 - 5 - 7 + 6)^3 \\
 \mathbf{469097433} &:= (4 + 690 + 9 + 74 + 3 - 3)^3 \\
 &:= (4 + 690 + 9 + 74 - 3 + 3)^3 \\
 \mathbf{472729139} &:= (47 - 2 + 729 - 1 - 3 + 9)^3 \\
 \mathbf{476379541} &:= (4 + 763 + 7 + 9 - 5 + 4 - 1)^3 \\
 \mathbf{478211768} &:= (-47 + 821 - 1 + 7 - 6 + 8)^3 \\
 &:= (-47 + 821 + 1 - 7 + 6 + 8)^3 \\
 &:= (-4 + 782 + 11 + 7 - 6 - 8)^3 \\
 &:= (4 + 782 - 11 - 7 + 6 + 8)^3 \\
 &:= (-4 + 782 + 1 + 17 - 6 - 8)^3 \\
 &:= (4 + 782 - 1 - 17 + 6 + 8)^3 \\
 &:= (4 - 7 + 8 - 2 + 11 + 768)^3 \\
 \mathbf{479785216} &:= (47 + 97 + 8 + 5 - 2 - 1 - 6)^4 \\
 &:= (47 + 97 - 8 + 5 + 2 - 1 + 6)^4 \\
 &:= (47 + 9 + 78 + 5 + 2 + 1 + 6)^4 \\
 &:= (-4 + 79 - 7 + 85 + 2 - 1 - 6)^4
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 &:= (4 + 7 + 97 + 8 + 5 + 21 + 6)^4 \\
 &:= (47 - 9 + 78 + 5 + 21 + 6)^4 \\
 &:= (47 + 9 - 7 + 85 - 2 + 16)^4 \\
 &:= (47 - 9 + 7 + 85 + 2 + 16)^4 \\
 &:= (4 + 79 + 78 + 5 - 2 - 16)^4 \\
 &:= (4 + 79 + 7 + 85 - 21 - 6)^4 \\
 &:= (4 + 7 - 9 + 78 + 52 + 16)^4 \\
 \mathbf{480048687} &:= (4 + 800 - 4 - 8 + 6 - 8 - 7)^3 \\
 &:= (-4 + 800 + 4 - 8 + 6 - 8 - 7)^3 \\
 &:= (4 + 80 + 04 + 8 + 687)^3 \\
 &:= (48 + 0048 + 687)^3 \\
 &:= (-4 + 800 + 48 - 68 + 7)^3 \\
 \mathbf{481890304} &:= (4 + 8 + 18 - 9 + 03 + 04)^6 \\
 &:= (-4 + 8 - 1 + 8 - 9 + 030 - 4)^6 \\
 &:= (4 + 8 - 1 - 8 - 9 + 030 + 4)^6 \\
 &:= (4 - 8 - 1 + 8 - 9 + 030 + 4)^6 \\
 &:= (48 - 18 - 9 + 03 + 04)^6 \\
 &:= (-48 + 1 - 8 + 90 - 3 - 04)^6 \\
 &:= (4 - 81 + 8 + 90 + 3 + 04)^6 \\
 &:= (481 + 8 - 9 + 0304)^3 \\
 \mathbf{483736625} &:= (4 + 837 + 3 - 66 + 2 + 5)^3 \\
 &:= (-4 + 837 + 3 + 6 - 62 + 5)^3 \\
 &:= (48 - 3 + 73 + 662 + 5)^3 \\
 \mathbf{484220025} &:= (4 + 8 - 4 + 22002 - 5)^2 \\
 &:= (-4 + 8 + 4 + 22002 - 5)^2 \\
 \mathbf{485587656} &:= (4 + 855 - 8 - 76 + 5 + 6)^3 \\
 &:= (-4 + 855 - 8 - 7 + 6 - 56)^3 \\
 &:= (-48 + 55 + 8 + 765 + 6)^3 \\
 &:= (-48 + 5 + 58 + 765 + 6)^3 \\
 &:= (-4 - 8 + 55 + 87 + 656)^3 \\
 \mathbf{487443403} &:= (4 + 8 + 744 + 34 - 03)^3 \\
 \mathbf{489303872} &:= (4 + 8 - 93 - 03 + 872)^3 \\
 &:= (-48 - 9 - 30 + 3 + 872)^3 \\
 \mathbf{491169069} &:= (4 + 91 + 1 + 690 - 6 + 9)^3 \\
 \mathbf{492884401} &:= (-4 + 92 + 8 + 8 + 44 + 01)^4 \\
 &:= (4 + 92 + 8 + 8 - 4 + 40 + 1)^4 \\
 &:= (-4 + 92 + 8 + 8 + 4 + 40 + 1)^4 \\
 &:= (4 + 92 + 88 + 4 - 40 + 1)^4 \\
 &:= (4 + 92 + 8 + 84 - 40 + 1)^4 \\
 \mathbf{493817284} &:= (4938 + 17284)^2 \\
 \mathbf{494217361} &:= (494 + 21736 + 1)^2 \\
 \mathbf{494913671} &:= (-49 + 4 + 913 - 6 - 71)^3 \\
 &:= (4 + 94 + 9 + 13 + 671)^3 \\
 \mathbf{496793088} &:= (-4 + 9 - 6 + 793 + 08 - 8)^3 \\
 &:= (-4 + 9 - 6 + 793 - 08 + 8)^3 \\
 &:= (-49 + 6 - 7 + 930 - 88)^3 \\
 &:= (4 - 9 + 679 + 30 + 88)^3 \\
 \mathbf{498677257} &:= (-4 + 9 + 8 + 6 + 772 - 5 + 7)^3 \\
 &:= (4 - 9 + 8 + 6 + 772 + 5 + 7)^3 \\
 &:= (4 + 98 + 677 + 2 + 5 + 7)^3 \\
 &:= (-49 + 867 + 7 - 25 - 7)^3 \\
 &:= (-49 + 867 - 7 - 25 + 7)^3 \\
 &:= (49 + 8 + 677 + 2 + 57)^3 \\
 \mathbf{503284375} &:= (5 + 03 + 28 + 4 + 3 + 7 + 5)^5 \\
 &:= (5 + 03 - 2 + 8 + 43 - 7 + 5)^5 \\
 &:= (50 + 32 - 8 - 4 - 3 - 7 - 5)^5 \\
 &:= (-5 + 032 - 8 + 4 + 37 - 5)^5 \\
 &:= (5 - 032 + 8 - 4 + 3 + 75)^5 \\
 &:= (50 - 32 - 8 + 43 + 7 - 5)^5 \\
 &:= (50 - 3 - 28 + 4 + 37 - 5)^5 \\
 &:= (-50 + 3 + 28 - 4 + 3 + 75)^5 \\
 &:= (50 - 3 + 2 + 84 - 3 - 75)^5 \\
 &:= (-50 - 3 - 2 - 8 + 43 + 75)^5 \\
 &:= (503 + 2 - 8 - 437 - 5)^5 \\
 \mathbf{504358336} &:= (5 - 043 - 5 + 833 + 6)^3 \\
 &:= (-5 - 043 + 5 + 833 + 6)^3 \\
 &:= (-5043 + 5833 + 6)^3 \\
 \mathbf{510082399} &:= (-5 - 1 + 00823 - 9 - 9)^3 \\
 \mathbf{513922401} &:= (5 + 1 + 392 + 2 + 401)^3 \\
 \mathbf{517781627} &:= (5 - 1 + 7 + 781 + 6 - 2 + 7)^3 \\
 &:= (-5 + 1 + 7 - 7 + 816 - 2 - 7)^3 \\
 &:= (-5 + 1 - 7 + 7 + 816 - 2 - 7)^3 \\
 &:= (5 + 1 - 7 - 7 + 816 + 2 - 7)^3 \\
 &:= (-5 + 1 - 7 - 7 + 816 - 2 + 7)^3 \\
 &:= (5 - 1 + 778 + 16 - 2 + 7)^3 \\
 &:= (-5 - 1 + 7 + 781 - 6 + 27)^3
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 &:= (-5 + 1 - 7 + 781 + 6 + 27)^3 \\
 \mathbf{519885601} &:= (51 + 98 - 8 + 5 + 6 - 01)^4 \\
 &:= (5 + 1 + 98 - 8 + 56 - 01)^4 \\
 &:= (5 - 1 + 98 - 8 + 56 + 01)^4 \\
 &:= (5 + 1 - 9 + 88 + 5 + 60 + 1)^4 \\
 &:= (5 + 1 + 9 - 8 + 85 + 60 - 1)^4 \\
 &:= (5 - 1 + 9 - 8 + 85 + 60 + 1)^4 \\
 &:= (5 + 1 - 9 + 8 + 85 + 60 + 1)^4 \\
 \mathbf{521660125} &:= (-5 + 216 + 601 - 2 - 5)^3 \\
 \mathbf{522853956} &:= (5 + 22853 + 9 + 5 - 6)^2 \\
 \mathbf{525557943} &:= (-5 + 25 - 5 - 5 + 794 + 3)^3 \\
 \mathbf{527514112} &:= (52 + 751 - 4 + 11 - 2)^3 \\
 \mathbf{529230025} &:= (5 + 2 - 9 + 23002 + 5)^2 \\
 \mathbf{529475129} &:= (52 + 9 + 4 + 751 + 2 - 9)^3 \\
 &:= (52 - 9 + 4 + 751 + 2 + 9)^3 \\
 &:= (5 + 294 + 7 + 512 - 9)^3 \\
 &:= (-5 - 2 + 94 + 751 - 29)^3 \\
 \mathbf{533411731} &:= (5 + 33 + 41 + 1 + 731)^3 \\
 \mathbf{533794816} &:= (53 + 3 + 79 + 4 + 8 - 1 + 6)^4 \\
 &:= (53 - 3 + 7 + 94 + 8 - 1 - 6)^4 \\
 &:= (53 - 3 - 7 + 94 + 8 + 1 + 6)^4 \\
 &:= (5 + 33 + 7 + 94 + 8 - 1 + 6)^4 \\
 &:= (5 + 3 + 37 + 94 + 8 - 1 + 6)^4 \\
 &:= (53 + 37 + 9 + 48 - 1 + 6)^4 \\
 &:= (53 + 37 - 9 - 4 + 81 - 6)^4 \\
 &:= (5 + 3 - 37 + 94 + 81 + 6)^4 \\
 &:= (5 - 337 + 9 + 481 - 6)^4 \\
 \mathbf{535387328} &:= (-53 + 5 - 3 + 873 - 2 - 8)^3 \\
 &:= (-53 - 5 + 3 + 873 + 2 - 8)^3 \\
 &:= (5 - 3 - 53 + 873 - 2 - 8)^3 \\
 &:= (-5 + 3 - 53 + 873 + 2 - 8)^3 \\
 &:= (5 - 35 - 3 + 873 - 28)^3 \\
 \mathbf{536870912} &:= (5 - 3 + 6 + 8 + 7 - 09 - 12)^{29} \\
 &:= (-5 + 3 + 6 + 8 - 7 + 09 - 12)^{29} \\
 &:= (5 + 3 + 6 - 8 - 7 - 09 + 12)^{29} \\
 &:= (-5 - 3 + 6 + 8 - 7 - 09 + 12)^{29} \\
 &:= (5 - 3 - 6 - 8 - 7 + 09 + 12)^{29} \\
 &:= (53 - 68 + 7 + 09 - 1 + 2)^{29}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 &:= (-53 + 68 - 7 - 09 + 1 + 2)^{29} \\
 &:= (-5 + 3 + 68 - 70 + 9 - 1 - 2)^{29} \\
 &:= (-5 - 3 - 68 + 70 + 9 + 1 - 2)^{29} \\
 &:= (5 + 3 - 68 + 70 - 9 - 1 + 2)^{29} \\
 &:= (-5 - 3 + 68 - 70 + 9 + 1 + 2)^{29} \\
 &:= (5 - 3 + 6 + 87 - 091 - 2)^{29} \\
 &:= (-5 + 3 + 6 + 87 - 091 + 2)^{29} \\
 &:= (5 - 3 - 6 - 87 + 091 + 2)^{29} \\
 &:= (53 + 6 - 8 - 70 + 9 + 12)^{29} \\
 \mathbf{537367797} &:= (-5 + 37 + 3 + 6 + 779 - 7)^3 \\
 &:= (-5 + 37 - 3 - 6 - 7 + 797)^3 \\
 &:= (-5 + 3 + 736 + 77 + 9 - 7)^3 \\
 &:= (5 - 3 + 736 + 77 - 9 + 7)^3 \\
 &:= (-5 + 3 + 736 + 7 + 79 - 7)^3 \\
 &:= (-5 + 3 + 736 - 7 + 79 + 7)^3 \\
 &:= (-5 + 3 + 7 + 36 + 779 - 7)^3 \\
 &:= (-5 + 3 - 7 + 36 + 779 + 7)^3 \\
 &:= (5 + 37 - 3 + 677 + 97)^3 \\
 \mathbf{539353144} &:= (539 - 35 + 314 - 4)^3 \\
 \mathbf{543338496} &:= (5 + 4 - 33 - 3 + 849 - 6)^3 \\
 &:= (-5 - 4 - 33 + 3 + 849 + 6)^3 \\
 &:= (5 + 4 - 3 - 33 + 849 - 6)^3 \\
 &:= (-5 - 4 + 3 - 33 + 849 + 6)^3 \\
 \mathbf{545338513} &:= (5 - 4 - 5 - 33 + 851 + 3)^3 \\
 &:= (-5 - 4 + 5 - 33 + 851 + 3)^3 \\
 \mathbf{547981281} &:= (54 + 79 + 8 + 1 + 2 + 8 + 1)^4 \\
 &:= (54 + 7 + 98 + 1 + 2 - 8 - 1)^4 \\
 &:= (54 - 7 + 98 - 1 + 2 + 8 - 1)^4 \\
 &:= (54 + 7 + 98 - 1 + 2 - 8 + 1)^4 \\
 &:= (54 - 7 + 98 + 1 - 2 + 8 + 1)^4 \\
 &:= (5 + 47 + 9 + 81 + 2 + 8 + 1)^4 \\
 &:= (5 + 47 + 9 + 8 + 1 + 2 + 81)^4 \\
 &:= (5 + 4 - 7 - 9 + 81 - 2 + 81)^4 \\
 &:= (-5 - 4 - 7 + 9 + 81 - 2 + 81)^4 \\
 &:= (-5 - 4 + 7 - 9 + 81 + 2 + 81)^4 \\
 &:= (54 + 79 - 8 + 1 + 28 - 1)^4 \\
 &:= (54 + 79 - 8 - 1 + 28 + 1)^4 \\
 &:= (54 + 7 - 9 + 8 + 12 + 81)^4
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 &:= (5 + 47 + 98 + 12 - 8 - 1)^4 \\
 &:= (5 + 47 - 9 + 81 + 28 + 1)^4 \\
 &:= (-547 + 981 - 281)^4 \\
 \mathbf{549353259} &:= (549 + 3 + 5 + 3 + 259)^3 \\
 &:= (5 + 493 + 5 + 325 - 9)^3 \\
 \mathbf{550731776} &:= (55 + 07 + 3 - 1 - 7 - 7 + 6)^5 \\
 &:= (55 - 07 + 3 - 1 + 7 - 7 + 6)^5 \\
 &:= (55 - 07 + 3 - 1 - 7 + 7 + 6)^5 \\
 &:= (-5 + 50 + 7 - 3 - 1 + 7 + 7 - 6)^5 \\
 &:= (5 + 50 + 7 + 3 - 1 - 7 - 7 + 6)^5 \\
 &:= (5 + 50 - 7 + 3 - 1 + 7 - 7 + 6)^5 \\
 &:= (-5 + 50 + 7 - 3 + 1 + 7 - 7 + 6)^5 \\
 &:= (5 + 50 - 7 + 3 - 1 - 7 + 7 + 6)^5 \\
 &:= (-5 + 50 + 7 - 3 + 1 - 7 + 7 + 6)^5 \\
 &:= (-5 + 50 - 7 - 3 + 1 + 7 + 7 + 6)^5 \\
 &:= (-5 - 5 + 073 - 1 + 7 - 7 - 6)^5 \\
 &:= (-5 - 5 + 073 - 1 - 7 + 7 - 6)^5 \\
 &:= (-5 - 5 + 073 + 1 - 7 - 7 + 6)^5 \\
 &:= (5 + 5 + 07 + 31 + 7 + 7 - 6)^5 \\
 &:= (-5 - 5 - 07 + 3 - 1 + 77 - 6)^5 \\
 &:= (-5 - 5 - 07 + 3 + 1 - 7 + 76)^5 \\
 &:= (55 + 073 - 1 - 77 + 6)^5 \\
 &:= (5 + 50 + 73 - 1 - 77 + 6)^5 \\
 &:= (-5 + 50 - 73 + 1 + 77 + 6)^5 \\
 &:= (-5 + 50 - 73 + 1 + 7 + 76)^5 \\
 \mathbf{551368000} &:= (5 + 5 + 1 + 3 + 6 + 800 + 0)^3 \\
 &:= (55 + 1 - 36 + 800 + 0)^3 \\
 &:= (5 + 51 - 36 + 800 + 0)^3 \\
 \mathbf{553387661} &:= (5 - 5 + 3 + 3 + 876 - 61)^3 \\
 &:= (-5 + 5 + 3 + 3 + 876 - 61)^3 \\
 \mathbf{559476224} &:= (55 + 9 + 4 + 762 - 2 - 4)^3 \\
 &:= (55 + 9 - 4 + 762 - 2 + 4)^3 \\
 &:= (5 + 59 + 4 + 762 - 2 - 4)^3 \\
 &:= (5 + 59 - 4 + 762 - 2 + 4)^3 \\
 &:= (-55 + 947 - 62 - 2 - 4)^3 \\
 &:= (5 + 594 + 7 - 6 + 224)^3 \\
 &:= (559 + 47 - 6 + 224)^3 \\
 \mathbf{562448656} &:= (5 + 62 + 4 - 4 + 86 - 5 + 6)^4 \\
 &:= (5 + 62 - 4 + 4 + 86 - 5 + 6)^4 \\
 &:= (-5 + 62 + 4 - 4 + 86 + 5 + 6)^4 \\
 &:= (-5 + 62 - 4 + 4 + 86 + 5 + 6)^4 \\
 &:= (5 + 62 + 4 + 4 + 8 + 65 + 6)^4 \\
 &:= (5 + 6 + 2 + 44 + 86 + 5 + 6)^4 \\
 &:= (56 + 24 + 4 + 8 + 6 + 56)^4 \\
 &:= (-5 - 6 + 244 - 8 - 65 - 6)^4 \\
 &:= (5 + 6 + 24 + 48 + 65 + 6)^4 \\
 &:= (5 + 624 - 486 + 5 + 6)^4 \\
 &:= (-56 + 2 - 448 + 656)^4 \\
 \mathbf{563559976} &:= (-56 - 35 - 59 + 976)^3 \\
 \mathbf{569722789} &:= (56 - 9 - 7 + 2 - 2 + 789)^3 \\
 &:= (56 - 9 - 7 - 2 + 2 + 789)^3 \\
 &:= (5 + 6 + 9 + 722 + 78 + 9)^3 \\
 &:= (569 - 7 - 2 + 278 - 9)^3 \\
 \mathbf{571787000} &:= (-57 + 17 + 870 + 00)^3 \\
 \mathbf{573856191} &:= (5 - 7 - 3 + 856 - 19 - 1)^3 \\
 \mathbf{575930368} &:= (5 + 759 + 3 - 03 + 68)^3 \\
 &:= (5 + 759 - 3 + 03 + 68)^3 \\
 &:= (5 - 75 + 930 - 36 + 8)^3 \\
 \mathbf{576240025} &:= (-5 + 7 + 6 + 24002 - 5)^2 \\
 \mathbf{577200625} &:= (-57 - 7 + 200 - 6 + 25)^4 \\
 \mathbf{578009537} &:= (57 + 800 - 9 - 5 - 3 - 7)^3 \\
 &:= (-5 + 780 + 095 - 37)^3 \\
 \mathbf{582182875} &:= (-5 - 8 - 21 - 8 + 2 + 875)^3 \\
 &:= (-58 + 2 + 18 - 2 + 875)^3 \\
 &:= (-58 - 2 + 18 + 2 + 875)^3 \\
 \mathbf{584277056} &:= (5 + 842 + 7 - 7 - 05 - 6)^3 \\
 &:= (5 + 842 - 7 + 7 - 05 - 6)^3 \\
 &:= (-5 + 842 + 7 - 7 + 05 - 6)^3 \\
 &:= (-5 + 842 - 7 + 7 + 05 - 6)^3 \\
 &:= (-5 + 84 - 2 + 770 - 5 - 6)^3 \\
 &:= (5 + 8 + 42 + 770 + 5 + 6)^3 \\
 \mathbf{586376253} &:= (58 + 6 + 3 + 762 + 5 + 3)^3 \\
 &:= (-5 + 863 + 7 - 6 - 25 + 3)^3 \\
 &:= (5 + 8 + 6 + 3 + 762 + 53)^3 \\
 &:= (586 - 3 + 7 - 6 + 253)^3 \\
 &:= (-5 + 863 - 76 + 2 + 53)^3
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 \mathbf{588480472} &:= (-5 + 8 + 848 - 04 - 7 - 2)^3 & &:= (5 - 94 + 82 + 3 + 32 + 1)^6 \\
 &:= (5 + 8 + 8 + 4 + 804 + 7 + 2)^3 & &:= (-5 + 94 - 8 + 2 - 33 - 21)^6 \\
 &:= (-5 + 884 + 8 - 047 - 2)^3 & &:= (-5 - 9 + 48 - 23 - 3 + 21)^6 \\
 &:= (58 + 848 + 04 - 72)^3 & &:= (-5 + 9 - 4 + 823 - 3 + 21)^3 \\
 \mathbf{590589719} &:= (-5 + 905 - 8 + 9 - 71 + 9)^3 & &:= (5 - 9 + 4 + 823 - 3 + 21)^3 \\
 \mathbf{592240896} &:= (-59 - 2 + 240 - 8 - 9 - 6)^4 & &:= (5 + 94 - 82 + 33 - 21)^6 \\
 &:= (5 + 92 - 24 + 089 - 6)^4 & & \\
 \mathbf{594823321} &:= (5 + 9 + 4 + 8 + 2 + 3 - 3 + 2 - 1)^6 & & \\
 &:= (5 + 9 + 4 + 8 + 2 - 3 + 3 + 2 - 1)^6 & & \\
 &:= (5 + 9 + 4 + 8 - 2 + 3 + 3 - 2 + 1)^6 & & \\
 &:= (5 + 9 - 4 + 8 + 2 + 3 + 3 + 2 + 1)^6 & & \\
 &:= (-5 - 9 + 48 - 2 + 3 - 3 - 2 - 1)^6 & & \\
 &:= (-5 - 9 + 48 - 2 - 3 + 3 - 2 - 1)^6 & & \\
 &:= (-5 - 9 + 48 + 2 - 3 - 3 - 2 + 1)^6 & & \\
 &:= (-5 - 9 + 48 - 2 - 3 - 3 + 2 + 1)^6 & & \\
 &:= (-5 + 9 - 4 + 8 + 23 - 3 + 2 - 1)^6 & & \\
 &:= (5 - 9 + 4 + 8 + 23 - 3 + 2 - 1)^6 & & \\
 &:= (5 + 9 - 4 - 8 + 23 + 3 + 2 - 1)^6 & & \\
 &:= (5 + 9 + 4 - 8 + 23 - 3 - 2 + 1)^6 & & \\
 &:= (-5 + 9 + 4 - 8 + 23 + 3 + 2 + 1)^6 & & \\
 &:= (5 - 9 - 4 + 8 + 23 + 3 + 2 + 1)^6 & & \\
 &:= (-5 + 9 + 4 + 8 - 2 - 3 - 3 + 21)^6 & & \\
 &:= (5 + 9 + 4 - 8 - 2 + 3 - 3 + 21)^6 & & \\
 &:= (5 + 9 + 4 - 8 - 2 - 3 + 3 + 21)^6 & & \\
 &:= (-5 + 9 + 4 - 8 + 2 + 3 + 3 + 21)^6 & & \\
 &:= (5 - 9 - 4 + 8 + 2 + 3 + 3 + 21)^6 & & \\
 &:= (59 - 4 + 8 + 2 - 33 - 2 - 1)^6 & & \\
 &:= (59 - 4 + 8 - 2 - 33 + 2 - 1)^6 & & \\
 &:= (59 - 4 + 8 + 2 - 3 - 32 - 1)^6 & & \\
 &:= (59 + 4 - 8 + 2 + 3 - 32 + 1)^6 & & \\
 &:= (-5 + 9 + 48 - 23 + 3 - 2 - 1)^6 & & \\
 &:= (-5 + 9 + 48 - 23 - 3 + 2 + 1)^6 & & \\
 &:= (-5 + 9 + 48 - 2 + 3 - 3 - 21)^6 & & \\
 &:= (-5 + 9 + 48 - 2 - 3 + 3 - 21)^6 & & \\
 &:= (5 + 9 + 4 + 823 + 3 - 2 - 1)^3 & & \\
 &:= (5 + 9 + 4 + 823 - 3 + 2 + 1)^3 & & \\
 &:= (-5 - 9 + 4 - 8 + 23 + 3 + 21)^6 & & \\
 &:= (5 - 94 + 82 + 33 + 2 + 1)^6 & & \\
 \mathbf{596947688} &:= (59 - 6 + 9 + 4 + 768 + 8)^3 & & \\
 &:= (59 + 694 + 7 - 6 + 88)^3 & & \\
 &:= (59 - 6 + 94 + 7 + 688)^3 & & \\
 \mathbf{599077107} &:= (5 + 9 + 907 - 71 - 07)^3 & & \\
 \mathbf{601692057} &:= (6 - 01 + 6 - 9 - 2 + 057)^5 & & \\
 &:= (-6 + 01 - 6 + 9 + 2 + 057)^5 & & \\
 &:= (60 + 16 - 9 + 2 - 05 - 7)^5 & & \\
 &:= (60 - 16 + 9 + 2 - 05 + 7)^5 & & \\
 &:= (6 - 01 + 6 + 9 - 20 + 57)^5 & & \\
 &:= (-6 + 01 - 6 - 9 + 20 + 57)^5 & & \\
 &:= (60 - 16 - 9 + 20 - 5 + 7)^5 & & \\
 &:= (6 + 016 + 92 - 057)^5 & & \\
 \mathbf{605495736} &:= (6 + 05 + 4 + 95 + 736)^3 & & \\
 &:= (-60 - 54 + 957 - 3 + 6)^3 & & \\
 &:= (60 + 54 - 9 + 5 + 736)^3 & & \\
 &:= (605 - 495 + 736)^3 & & \\
 \mathbf{607573201} &:= (6 + 075 + 73 + 2 + 01)^4 & & \\
 &:= (60 + 7 + 57 + 32 + 01)^4 & & \\
 &:= (-60 + 7 + 5 + 7 - 3 + 201)^4 & & \\
 \mathbf{607645423} &:= (6 + 0764 + 54 + 23)^3 & & \\
 \mathbf{609800192} &:= (60 + 9 + 800 - 19 - 2)^3 & & \\
 &:= (60 + 980 - 0192)^3 & & \\
 \mathbf{611960049} &:= (-61 - 1 + 960 - 049)^3 & & \\
 \mathbf{612220032} &:= (6 + 1 + 2 + 2 + 2 + 003 + 2)^7 & & \\
 &:= (-6 - 1 + 22 + 2 + 003 - 2)^7 & & \\
 &:= (-6 + 1 + 22 + 2 - 003 + 2)^7 & & \\
 &:= (-6 - 1 + 22 - 2 + 003 + 2)^7 & & \\
 &:= (-6 - 1 + 2 + 22 + 003 - 2)^7 & & \\
 &:= (-6 + 1 + 2 + 22 - 003 + 2)^7 & & \\
 &:= (-6 - 1 - 2 + 22 + 003 + 2)^7 & & \\
 &:= (6 + 1 - 2 - 2 + 20 - 03 - 2)^7 & & \\
 &:= (-6 - 1 + 2 + 2 + 20 + 03 - 2)^7 & &
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 &:= (-6 + 1 + 2 + 2 + 20 - 03 + 2)^7 \\
 &:= (-6 - 1 + 2 - 2 + 20 + 03 + 2)^7 \\
 &:= (-6 - 1 - 2 + 2 + 20 + 03 + 2)^7 \\
 &:= (-6 - 12 + 2 + 2 + 0032)^7 \\
 &:= (61 - 22 - 20 - 03 + 2)^7 \\
 \mathbf{618470208} &:= (-6 + 1 + 847 + 02 + 08)^3 \\
 &:= (-6 - 1 + 847 + 020 - 8)^3 \\
 \mathbf{622835864} &:= (6 + 2 - 2 - 8 - 3 - 5 + 864)^3 \\
 &:= (6 - 2 + 2 - 8 - 3 - 5 + 864)^3 \\
 &:= (-6 - 2 - 2 + 8 - 3 - 5 + 864)^3 \\
 &:= (-6 - 2 - 2 - 8 + 3 + 5 + 864)^3 \\
 &:= (6 - 22 + 8 + 3 - 5 + 864)^3 \\
 \mathbf{623201296} &:= (62 + 3 - 2 + 01 - 2 + 96)^4 \\
 &:= (62 - 3 + 2 - 01 + 2 + 96)^4 \\
 \mathbf{626250625} &:= (-6 - 26 + 25062 - 5)^2 \\
 \mathbf{627222016} &:= (627 + 222 + 01 + 6)^3 \\
 &:= (627 + 2 + 220 + 1 + 6)^3 \\
 &:= (627 + 22 + 201 + 6)^3 \\
 \mathbf{629422793} &:= (-6 - 2 + 94 - 22 + 793)^3 \\
 \mathbf{631628712} &:= (6 - 3 - 16 + 2 + 871 - 2)^3 \\
 &:= (6 - 3 - 16 - 2 + 871 + 2)^3 \\
 \mathbf{633839779} &:= (63 + 3 + 8 - 3 + 9 + 779)^3 \\
 &:= (63 - 3 + 8 + 3 + 9 + 779)^3 \\
 &:= (6 + 3 - 3 + 83 - 9 + 779)^3 \\
 &:= (6 - 3 + 3 + 83 - 9 + 779)^3 \\
 &:= (-6 - 3 - 3 + 83 + 9 + 779)^3 \\
 &:= (-63 - 3 + 839 + 77 + 9)^3 \\
 &:= (-63 - 3 + 839 + 7 + 79)^3 \\
 &:= (6 - 3 + 38 + 39 + 779)^3 \\
 \mathbf{638277381} &:= (-6 + 3 + 82 + 773 + 8 + 1)^3 \\
 &:= (-6 + 3 + 8 + 2 + 773 + 81)^3 \\
 \mathbf{639128961} &:= (63 + 9 + 1 + 2 + 89 - 6 + 1)^4 \\
 &:= (6 - 3 + 9 - 1 - 2 + 89 + 61)^4 \\
 &:= (-6 + 3 + 9 + 1 + 2 + 89 + 61)^4 \\
 &:= (6 + 39 + 128 - 9 - 6 + 1)^4 \\
 &:= (-6 + 39 + 128 - 9 + 6 + 1)^4 \\
 &:= (-6 + 39 + 1 + 28 + 96 + 1)^4 \\
 \mathbf{640503928} &:= (-64 - 05 + 03 + 928)^3 \\
 \mathbf{642825316} &:= (6 + 4 + 28 + 25316)^2 \\
 \mathbf{644972544} &:= (-6 - 44 + 972 - 54 - 4)^3 \\
 \mathbf{649461896} &:= (-6 - 4 - 9 - 4 - 6 - 1 + 896)^3 \\
 &:= (6 - 4 + 946 + 1 - 89 + 6)^3 \\
 &:= (-6 + 4 + 946 + 18 - 96)^3 \\
 \mathbf{656234909} &:= (-65 + 6 + 23 - 4 + 909)^3 \\
 \mathbf{656356768} &:= (65 + 6 - 3 + 5 + 6 - 7 - 6 - 8)^5 \\
 &:= (65 + 6 - 3 + 5 - 6 - 7 + 6 - 8)^5 \\
 &:= (65 - 6 - 3 + 5 + 6 - 7 + 6 - 8)^5 \\
 &:= (65 + 6 + 3 - 5 - 6 - 7 - 6 + 8)^5 \\
 &:= (65 - 6 + 3 - 5 + 6 - 7 - 6 + 8)^5 \\
 &:= (65 - 6 + 3 - 5 - 6 - 7 + 6 + 8)^5 \\
 &:= (6 - 5 + 63 - 5 + 6 + 7 - 6 - 8)^5 \\
 &:= (6 - 5 + 63 - 5 - 6 + 7 + 6 - 8)^5 \\
 &:= (-6 - 5 + 63 - 5 + 6 + 7 + 6 - 8)^5 \\
 &:= (6 + 5 + 63 - 5 - 6 - 7 - 6 + 8)^5 \\
 &:= (6 - 5 + 63 + 5 - 6 - 7 - 6 + 8)^5 \\
 &:= (-6 + 5 + 63 - 5 + 6 - 7 - 6 + 8)^5 \\
 &:= (-6 - 5 + 63 + 5 + 6 - 7 - 6 + 8)^5 \\
 &:= (-6 + 5 + 63 - 5 - 6 - 7 + 6 + 8)^5 \\
 &:= (-6 - 5 + 63 + 5 - 6 - 7 + 6 + 8)^5 \\
 &:= (6 - 5 + 6 + 3 - 5 + 67 - 6 - 8)^5 \\
 &:= (6 - 5 - 6 + 3 - 5 + 67 + 6 - 8)^5 \\
 &:= (-6 - 5 + 6 + 3 - 5 + 67 + 6 - 8)^5 \\
 &:= (6 + 5 - 6 + 3 - 5 - 6 - 7 + 68)^5 \\
 &:= (-6 + 5 + 6 + 3 - 5 - 6 - 7 + 68)^5 \\
 &:= (6 - 5 - 6 + 3 + 5 - 6 - 7 + 68)^5 \\
 &:= (-6 - 5 + 6 + 3 + 5 - 6 - 7 + 68)^5 \\
 &:= (-6 + 5 - 6 + 3 - 5 + 6 - 7 + 68)^5 \\
 &:= (-6 - 5 - 6 + 3 + 5 + 6 - 7 + 68)^5 \\
 &:= (-6 + 56 + 35 - 6 - 7 - 6 - 8)^5 \\
 &:= (-65 + 63 - 5 + 67 + 6 - 8)^5 \\
 &:= (65 + 63 - 5 - 67 - 6 + 8)^5 \\
 &:= (-65 + 63 + 5 - 6 - 7 + 68)^5 \\
 &:= (65 - 6 + 3 - 5 - 67 + 68)^5 \\
 &:= (-6 + 56 + 3 - 56 - 7 + 68)^5 \\
 &:= (-6 - 56 + 3 + 56 - 7 + 68)^5 \\
 &:= (6 - 5 + 63 - 5 + 67 - 68)^5
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 & := (-6 + 5 + 63 - 5 - 67 + 68)^5 \\
 & := (-6 - 5 + 63 + 5 - 67 + 68)^5 \\
 & := (-6 + 563 - 567 + 68)^5 \\
 \mathbf{663054848} & := (6 + 6 + 3 + 05 + 4 + 848)^3 \\
 & := (6 - 6 - 30 + 54 + 848)^3 \\
 & := (-6 + 6 - 30 + 54 + 848)^3 \\
 \mathbf{665338617} & := (6 - 6 + 5 + 3 - 3 + 861 + 7)^3 \\
 & := (-6 + 6 + 5 + 3 - 3 + 861 + 7)^3 \\
 & := (6 - 6 + 5 - 3 + 3 + 861 + 7)^3 \\
 & := (-6 + 6 + 5 - 3 + 3 + 861 + 7)^3 \\
 \mathbf{667627624} & := (6 + 6 + 762 + 76 + 24)^3 \\
 \mathbf{669921875} & := (6 + 6 + 9 + 921 + 8 - 75)^3 \\
 \mathbf{671898241} & := (67 - 1 - 8 + 98 + 2 + 4 - 1)^4 \\
 & := (67 + 1 - 8 + 98 - 2 + 4 + 1)^4 \\
 & := (-6 + 71 + 89 + 8 + 2 - 4 + 1)^4 \\
 & := (6 + 71 + 89 - 8 - 2 + 4 + 1)^4 \\
 & := (6 + 71 + 8 - 9 + 82 + 4 - 1)^4 \\
 & := (-6 + 71 + 8 + 9 + 82 - 4 + 1)^4 \\
 & := (-6 - 7 + 189 - 8 - 2 - 4 - 1)^4 \\
 & := (6 + 7 - 1 + 8 + 98 + 2 + 41)^4 \\
 & := (67 + 18 - 9 + 82 + 4 - 1)^4 \\
 & := (-6 - 7 + 189 + 8 - 24 + 1)^4 \\
 & := (6 + 7 + 189 - 82 + 41)^4 \\
 \mathbf{676836152} & := (-6 + 768 + 3 + 61 + 52)^3 \\
 & := (-6 + 768 - 36 + 152)^3 \\
 \mathbf{677925369} & := (677 - 9 + 25369)^2 \\
 \mathbf{679151439} & := (6 - 7 + 915 - 1 - 43 + 9)^3 \\
 \mathbf{679151439} & := (-6 + 791 + 51 + 4 + 39)^3 \\
 \mathbf{681472000} & := (-6 + 814 + 72 + 000)^3 \\
 \mathbf{683797841} & := (6 + 8 + 3 + 7 + 9 + 7 + 841)^3 \\
 & := (68 + 3 + 797 + 8 + 4 + 1)^3 \\
 & := (6 + 83 + 797 - 8 + 4 - 1)^3 \\
 & := (6 - 8 + 3 + 797 + 84 - 1)^3 \\
 & := (-6 + 8 - 3 + 797 + 84 + 1)^3 \\
 & := (6 + 8 + 3 + 79 + 784 + 1)^3 \\
 & := (68 + 37 - 9 + 784 + 1)^3 \\
 & := (683 + 79 + 78 + 41)^3 \\
 \mathbf{686128968} & := (6 + 861 + 2 + 8 - 9 + 6 + 8)^3 \\
 \mathbf{688465387} & := (6 + 884 + 6 + 5 - 3 - 8 - 7)^3 \\
 & := (6 + 884 - 6 - 5 + 3 + 8 - 7)^3 \\
 & := (-6 + 884 + 6 - 5 + 3 + 8 - 7)^3 \\
 & := (6 + 8 + 846 + 5 + 3 + 8 + 7)^3 \\
 \mathbf{688747536} & := (68 + 87 + 4 + 7 + 5 - 3 - 6)^4 \\
 & := (68 + 87 - 4 + 7 - 5 + 3 + 6)^4 \\
 & := (6 + 88 + 7 + 47 + 5 + 3 + 6)^4 \\
 & := (6 + 8 + 87 + 47 + 5 + 3 + 6)^4 \\
 & := (6 + 8 + 8 + 74 + 75 - 3 - 6)^4 \\
 & := (-6 + 8 + 8 + 74 + 75 - 3 + 6)^4 \\
 & := (6 + 8 + 8 + 74 + 7 + 53 + 6)^4 \\
 & := (688 + 7 - 4 + 7 - 536)^4 \\
 \mathbf{693154125} & := (6 + 931 - 54 - 1 - 2 + 5)^3 \\
 \mathbf{695506456} & := (6 + 955 - 064 - 5 - 6)^3 \\
 & := (-6 + 955 - 064 - 5 + 6)^3 \\
 \mathbf{697864103} & := (-6 + 9 + 7 + 864 + 10 + 3)^3 \\
 \mathbf{702595369} & := (-70 - 2 + 5 + 953 - 6 + 9)^3 \\
 \mathbf{704969000} & := (704 + 96 + 90 + 00)^3 \\
 \mathbf{705911761} & := (70 + 5 + 91 - 1 - 7 + 6 - 1)^4 \\
 & := (70 + 5 + 9 + 1 + 1 + 76 + 1)^4 \\
 & := (-7 + 05 + 91 - 1 + 76 - 1)^4 \\
 & := (-7 + 05 - 9 - 1 + 176 - 1)^4 \\
 & := (70 + 5 + 9 + 11 + 7 + 61)^4 \\
 & := (70 + 5 + 9 + 1 + 17 + 61)^4 \\
 & := (-70 + 59 - 1 + 176 - 1)^4 \\
 \mathbf{707347971} & := (70 + 734 + 79 + 7 + 1)^3 \\
 & := (70 + 734 + 7 + 9 + 71)^3 \\
 & := (7 + 0734 + 79 + 71)^3 \\
 & := (707 + 34 + 79 + 71)^3 \\
 \mathbf{709732288} & := (7 + 0973 + 2 - 2 - 88)^3 \\
 & := (7 + 0973 - 2 + 2 - 88)^3 \\
 & := (709 + 73 + 22 + 88)^3 \\
 \mathbf{714924299} & := (7 - 1 + 49 + 2 + 4 - 2 + 9 - 9)^5 \\
 & := (7 - 1 + 49 - 2 + 4 + 2 + 9 - 9)^5 \\
 & := (7 - 1 + 49 + 2 + 4 - 2 - 9 + 9)^5 \\
 & := (7 - 1 + 49 - 2 + 4 + 2 - 9 + 9)^5 \\
 & := (-7 - 1 + 49 - 2 + 4 - 2 + 9 + 9)^5 \\
 & := (-7 - 1 + 49 + 2 - 4 + 2 + 9 + 9)^5
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 &:= (7-1+4+9+24-2+9+9)^5 \\
 &:= (7-1+4+9-2+42+9-9)^5 \\
 &:= (7-1+4+9-2+42-9+9)^5 \\
 &:= (7-1+4-9-2+42+9+9)^5 \\
 &:= (-7-1-4+9+2+42+9+9)^5 \\
 &:= (7-1+4+9-2+4+29+9)^5 \\
 &:= (-7-14+92+4+2-9-9)^5 \\
 &:= (7-1+49+24-2-9-9)^5 \\
 &:= (-7-1+49+2-4+29-9)^5 \\
 &:= (-7-1-4+9+24+29+9)^5 \\
 &:= (-71-4+92+42+9-9)^5 \\
 &:= (-71-4+92+42-9+9)^5 \\
 &:= (-71+4+92-4+29+9)^5 \\
 &:= (-71-4+92+4+29+9)^5 \\
 &:= (-71-4+9+24+2+99)^5 \\
 &:= (-71-4-9+2+42+99)^5 \\
 &:= (7-1+49+24-29+9)^5 \\
 &:= (7-1+4-92+42+99)^5 \\
 &:= (-71-4-9+242-99)^5 \\
 \mathbf{716917375} &:= (-7-16+917+3-7+5)^3 \\
 &:= (-7+169+1+737-5)^3 \\
 \mathbf{719323136} &:= (-7-1+932-31-3+6)^3 \\
 \mathbf{722695689} &:= (-72+26956+8-9)^2 \\
 \mathbf{723394816} &:= (72+3-3+9-4+81+6)^4 \\
 &:= (72-3+3+9-4+81+6)^4 \\
 &:= (-7+2+3-3+94+81-6)^4 \\
 &:= (-7+2-3+3+94+81-6)^4 \\
 &:= (72+3+3+94+8-16)^4 \\
 &:= (-7+233-9-48+1-6)^4 \\
 &:= (-7+233+9+4-81+6)^4 \\
 \mathbf{726572699} &:= (7+2+65+726+99)^3 \\
 &:= (7+265+726-99)^3 \\
 &:= (7+265-72+699)^3 \\
 \mathbf{733870808} &:= (7+3-3+87+0808)^3 \\
 &:= (7-3+3+87+0808)^3 \\
 &:= (-7-33+870+80-8)^3 \\
 \mathbf{736314327} &:= (736-3+143+27)^3 \\
 \mathbf{738763264} &:= (-7+3+876-32+64)^3 \\
 \mathbf{741200625} &:= (7-41+200+6-2-5)^4 \\
 &:= (-7-41+200+6+2+5)^4 \\
 &:= (-7+4-1+200-6-25)^4 \\
 \mathbf{748613312} &:= (7+4+861+33+1+2)^3 \\
 &:= (7+4+861+3+31+2)^3 \\
 \mathbf{751089429} &:= (7+5+10+894+2-9)^3 \\
 &:= (-7+5+10+894-2+9)^3 \\
 &:= (-7+51+0894-29)^3 \\
 \mathbf{751527396} &:= (7+5+1+5+27396)^2 \\
 \mathbf{753571000} &:= (-75-3-5-7+1000)^3 \\
 &:= (753+57+100+0)^3 \\
 \mathbf{759333136} &:= (75+93+3+3+1-3-6)^4 \\
 &:= (75+93+3-3+1+3-6)^4 \\
 &:= (75+93-3+3+1+3-6)^4 \\
 &:= (75+93-3-3+1-3+6)^4 \\
 &:= (7+5+9+3+3+3+136)^4 \\
 &:= (-75-93+331-3+6)^4 \\
 &:= (75+93+33+1-36)^4 \\
 &:= (75+93+3+31-36)^4 \\
 &:= (75-9+33+31+36)^4 \\
 &:= (75-9-33-3+136)^4 \\
 &:= (7+59+33+31+36)^4 \\
 &:= (7+59-33-3+136)^4 \\
 &:= (7+59-3-33+136)^4 \\
 \mathbf{761048497} &:= (76-1-04+849-7)^3 \\
 \mathbf{763551944} &:= (7-6-35+5-1+944)^3 \\
 &:= (-7+6-35+5+1+944)^3 \\
 &:= (7+6+3+5-51+944)^3 \\
 \mathbf{768575296} &:= (76+85+752+9-6)^3 \\
 \mathbf{776151559} &:= (7+761+5+155-9)^3 \\
 \mathbf{777796321} &:= (77+77+9+6-3+2-1)^4 \\
 &:= (77+7+79+6-3+2-1)^4 \\
 &:= (77+7-7+96-3-2-1)^4 \\
 &:= (77-7+7+96-3-2-1)^4 \\
 &:= (7+77+79+6-3+2-1)^4 \\
 &:= (7+77-7+96-3-2-1)^4 \\
 &:= (-7+77+7+96-3-2-1)^4
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 &:= (7 - 7 + 77 + 96 - 3 - 2 - 1)^4 \\
 &:= (-7 + 7 + 77 + 96 - 3 - 2 - 1)^4 \\
 &:= (77 - 7 + 79 - 6 + 3 + 21)^4 \\
 &:= (-7 + 77 + 79 - 6 + 3 + 21)^4 \\
 \mathbf{781229961} &:= (7 + 812 - 2 + 99 + 6 - 1)^3 \\
 &:= (7 + 812 - 2 + 9 + 96 - 1)^3 \\
 &:= (7 - 81 + 2 - 2 + 996 - 1)^3 \\
 &:= (7 - 81 - 2 + 2 + 996 - 1)^3 \\
 &:= (-7 + 8 - 12 - 29 + 961)^3 \\
 \mathbf{783777448} &:= (783 + 77 + 74 - 4 - 8)^3 \\
 &:= (-7 + 8377 - 7448)^3 \\
 \mathbf{786330467} &:= (786 - 330 + 467)^3 \\
 \mathbf{788889024} &:= (-78 + 88 + 8 + 902 + 4)^3 \\
 &:= (-78 + 8 + 88 + 902 + 4)^3 \\
 &:= (-78 + 888 + 90 + 24)^3 \\
 &:= (-78 + 88 + 890 + 24)^3 \\
 \mathbf{791128129} &:= (7 - 9 + 1 - 1 + 28129)^2 \\
 &:= (7 - 9 - 1 + 1 + 28129)^2 \\
 \mathbf{791453125} &:= (7 + 914 + 5 + 3 - 1 + 2 - 5)^3 \\
 &:= (7 + 914 + 5 - 3 - 1 - 2 + 5)^3 \\
 &:= (7 + 914 - 5 + 3 - 1 + 2 + 5)^3 \\
 &:= (-7 + 914 - 5 - 3 + 1 + 25)^3 \\
 \mathbf{796594176} &:= (79 + 6 - 5 + 9 + 4 - 1 + 76)^4 \\
 &:= (79 - 6 + 5 + 9 + 4 + 1 + 76)^4 \\
 &:= (7 + 96 + 59 + 4 + 1 + 7 - 6)^4 \\
 &:= (7 + 96 - 5 - 9 + 4 - 1 + 76)^4 \\
 &:= (7 - 9 + 6 - 5 + 94 - 1 + 76)^4 \\
 &:= (7 - 9 - 6 + 5 + 94 + 1 + 76)^4 \\
 &:= (7 + 9 - 6 - 5 - 9 - 4 + 176)^4 \\
 &:= (7 - 9 - 6 - 5 + 9 - 4 + 176)^4 \\
 &:= (7 - 9 - 6 + 5 - 9 + 4 + 176)^4 \\
 &:= (79 + 65 + 9 + 4 + 17 - 6)^4 \\
 &:= (7 - 9 + 65 + 94 + 17 - 6)^4 \\
 &:= (7 - 9 - 6 + 59 + 41 + 76)^4 \\
 \mathbf{796597983} &:= (-7 + 9 - 65 + 979 + 8 + 3)^3 \\
 &:= (7 + 9 - 6 - 59 - 7 + 983)^3 \\
 &:= (-7 + 9 - 6 - 59 + 7 + 983)^3 \\
 &:= (79 - 6 + 59 + 798 - 3)^3
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 \mathbf{799178752} &:= (-79 + 917 + 87 + 5 - 2)^3 \\
 &:= (79 + 9 + 1 + 787 + 52)^3 \\
 &:= (7 - 9 + 91 + 787 + 52)^3 \\
 \mathbf{809557568} &:= (-80 + 955 - 7 + 56 + 8)^3 \\
 \mathbf{815730721} &:= (8 + 15 - 7 + 3 - 07 + 2 - 1)^8 \\
 &:= (-8 + 15 + 7 + 3 - 07 + 2 + 1)^8 \\
 &:= (-8 + 15 - 7 + 3 + 07 + 2 + 1)^8 \\
 &:= (8 - 15 + 7 + 3 + 07 + 2 + 1)^8 \\
 &:= (-8 - 1 - 5 + 7 + 30 - 7 - 2 - 1)^8 \\
 &:= (-8 - 1 - 5 - 7 + 30 + 7 - 2 - 1)^8 \\
 &:= (-8 - 1 + 5 - 7 + 30 - 7 + 2 - 1)^8 \\
 &:= (-8 + 1 + 5 - 7 + 30 - 7 - 2 + 1)^8 \\
 &:= (81 - 57 - 3 - 07 - 2 + 1)^8 \\
 &:= (81 - 5 - 73 + 07 + 2 + 1)^8 \\
 &:= (81 + 5 + 73 + 07 + 2 + 1)^4 \\
 &:= (81 - 5 + 7 + 3 - 072 - 1)^8 \\
 &:= (81 + 5 + 7 + 3 + 072 + 1)^4 \\
 &:= (8 + 15 + 7 - 3 + 07 - 21)^8 \\
 &:= (8 + 1 - 5 + 7 + 30 - 7 - 21)^8 \\
 &:= (8 + 1 - 5 - 7 + 30 + 7 - 21)^8 \\
 &:= (81 - 57 + 3 + 07 - 21)^8 \\
 &:= (81 + 57 + 3 + 07 + 21)^4 \\
 &:= (-8 + 157 + 30 - 7 - 2 - 1)^4 \\
 &:= (8 + 15 + 73 + 072 + 1)^4 \\
 &:= (-8 - 15 - 7 - 30 + 72 + 1)^8 \\
 &:= (8 + 1 + 57 + 30 + 72 + 1)^4 \\
 &:= (8 + 1 - 5 + 730 - 721)^8 \\
 \mathbf{817400375} &:= (817 + 40 + 03 + 75)^3 \\
 \mathbf{820025856} &:= (820 + 025 + 85 + 6)^3 \\
 &:= (820 + 02 + 58 + 56)^3 \\
 \mathbf{822656953} &:= (822 + 6 + 5 + 6 + 95 + 3)^3 \\
 &:= (822 + 65 + 6 - 9 + 53)^3 \\
 &:= (8 + 226 + 5 + 695 + 3)^3 \\
 \mathbf{825293672} &:= (-8 + 2 + 5 - 2 + 936 + 7 - 2)^3 \\
 &:= (-8 - 2 + 5 + 2 + 936 + 7 - 2)^3 \\
 &:= (8 + 2 - 5 + 2 + 936 - 7 + 2)^3 \\
 &:= (-8 - 2 + 5 - 2 + 936 + 7 + 2)^3 \\
 &:= (8 + 252 + 9 - 3 + 672)^3
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 \mathbf{827936019} &:= (8 - 2 + 7 + 936 - 01 - 9)^3 & &:= (8 + 75 + 2 + 1 + 30 + 56)^4 \\
 \mathbf{833237621} &:= (-8 + 332 + 3 - 7 + 621)^3 & &:= (8 - 7 + 52 + 130 - 5 - 6)^4 \\
 \mathbf{835896888} &:= (835 + 89 - 6 + 8 + 8 + 8)^3 & \mathbf{876467493} &:= (876 + 4 + 67 + 4 + 9 - 3)^3 \\
 &:= (835 + 8 + 9 - 6 + 88 + 8)^3 & \mathbf{876929769} &:= (-87 - 69 + 29769)^2 \\
 &:= (835 + 8 + 9 - 6 + 8 + 88)^3 & \mathbf{879217912} &:= (879 + 2 + 1 + 79 - 1 - 2)^3 \\
 &:= (8 + 35 + 8 + 9 - 6 + 888)^3 & &:= (879 + 2 - 1 + 79 + 1 - 2)^3 \\
 &:= (8 + 3 + 58 - 9 - 6 + 888)^3 & &:= (879 - 2 + 1 + 79 - 1 + 2)^3 \\
 \mathbf{843908625} &:= (843 + 9 + 086 + 2 + 5)^3 & &:= (879 - 2 - 1 + 79 + 1 + 2)^3 \\
 &:= (84 + 3 - 9 + 0862 + 5)^3 & &:= (879 - 2 - 1 - 7 + 91 - 2)^3 \\
 &:= (843 - 9 + 086 + 25)^3 & &:= (879 - 21 + 7 + 91 + 2)^3 \\
 \mathbf{844596301} &:= (8 - 4 - 4 + 59 + 6 - 3 - 01)^5 & \mathbf{881974079} &:= (8 - 8 + 1 + 974 - 07 - 9)^3 \\
 &:= (-8 + 4 + 4 + 59 + 6 - 3 - 01)^5 & &:= (-8 + 8 + 1 + 974 - 07 - 9)^3 \\
 &:= (-8 + 4 - 4 + 59 + 6 + 3 + 01)^5 & &:= (-8 - 8 - 1 + 974 - 07 + 9)^3 \\
 &:= (-8 - 4 + 4 + 59 + 6 + 3 + 01)^5 & \mathbf{887503681} &:= (8 - 8 - 7 + 50 + 3 - 6 - 8 - 1)^6 \\
 &:= (84 + 4 + 5 - 9 + 6 - 30 + 1)^5 & &:= (-8 + 8 - 7 + 50 + 3 - 6 - 8 - 1)^6 \\
 &:= (84 - 4 - 5 + 9 + 6 - 30 + 1)^5 & &:= (-8 - 8 - 7 + 50 + 3 - 6 + 8 - 1)^6 \\
 &:= (8 - 44 + 5 + 96 - 3 - 01)^5 & &:= (-8 - 8 + 7 + 50 + 3 - 6 - 8 + 1)^6 \\
 &:= (8 + 44 - 5 - 9 - 6 + 30 - 1)^5 & &:= (8 + 8 - 7 - 5 + 036 - 8 - 1)^6 \\
 &:= (8 + 4 - 45 + 96 - 3 + 01)^5 & &:= (8 - 8 - 7 - 5 + 036 + 8 - 1)^6 \\
 &:= (-8 - 4 + 45 - 9 + 6 + 30 + 1)^5 & &:= (-8 + 8 - 7 - 5 + 036 + 8 - 1)^6 \\
 &:= (-84 + 45 + 96 + 3 + 01)^5 & &:= (8 - 8 + 7 - 5 + 036 - 8 + 1)^6 \\
 \mathbf{846590536} &:= (8 - 4 + 6 - 5 + 905 + 36)^3 & &:= (-8 + 8 + 7 - 5 + 036 - 8 + 1)^6 \\
 &:= (846 + 59 + 05 + 36)^3 & &:= (-8 - 8 + 7 - 5 + 036 + 8 + 1)^6 \\
 &:= (8 + 4 + 65 + 905 - 36)^3 & &:= (88 - 75 + 03 + 6 + 8 + 1)^6 \\
 \mathbf{849278123} &:= (8 + 4 + 927 + 8 + 1 + 2 - 3)^3 & &:= (88 - 7 - 50 + 3 + 6 - 8 - 1)^6 \\
 &:= (8 + 4 + 927 + 8 - 1 - 2 + 3)^3 & &:= (88 - 7 - 50 - 3 - 6 + 8 + 1)^6 \\
 &:= (8 - 4 + 927 - 8 + 1 + 23)^3 & &:= (88 - 7 - 5 - 036 - 8 - 1)^6 \\
 &:= (-8 - 4 + 927 + 8 + 1 + 23)^3 & &:= (-8 + 87 - 50 + 3 + 6 - 8 + 1)^6 \\
 &:= (849 - 2 + 78 - 1 + 23)^3 & &:= (-8 + 87 - 5 - 036 - 8 + 1)^6 \\
 &:= (-84 + 927 + 81 + 23)^3 & &:= (8 + 8 - 75 + 03 + 6 + 81)^6 \\
 \mathbf{851971392} &:= (8 + 5 + 1 + 971 - 39 + 2)^3 & &:= (8 + 8 - 7 - 50 + 3 + 68 + 1)^6 \\
 \mathbf{865523177} &:= (865 + 5 + 2 + 3 + 1 + 77)^3 & &:= (8 + 8 - 7 - 50 - 3 - 6 + 81)^6 \\
 \mathbf{870983875} &:= (870 + 98 - 3 - 8 - 7 + 5)^3 & &:= (-8 - 8 + 7 - 50 + 3 + 6 + 81)^6 \\
 &:= (870 - 9 + 8 + 3 + 8 + 75)^3 & &:= (-8 - 8 + 7 - 5 - 036 + 81)^6 \\
 &:= (8 + 70 - 9 + 8 + 3 + 875)^3 & &:= (88 - 7 - 5 + 036 - 81)^6 \\
 &:= (-8 - 7 + 098 - 3 + 875)^3 & &:= (-88 + 7 - 5 + 036 + 81)^6 \\
 \mathbf{873722816} &:= (873 + 72 - 2 + 8 - 1 + 6)^3 & &:= (8 + 875 + 03 - 6 + 81)^3 \\
 \mathbf{875213056} &:= (87 + 5 + 21 + 3 + 056)^4 & \mathbf{890277128} &:= (890 + 2 + 77 - 1 + 2 - 8)^3
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 &:= (890 + 2 - 7 + 71 - 2 + 8)^3 \\
 &:= (890 - 2 - 7 + 71 + 2 + 8)^3 \\
 &:= (-8 + 902 + 77 + 1 - 2 - 8)^3 \\
 &:= (-8 + 902 + 7 + 71 - 2 - 8)^3 \\
 &:= (890 - 27 + 71 + 28)^3 \\
 \mathbf{893056347} &:= (8 + 930 + 5 + 6 + 3 + 4 + 7)^3 \\
 &:= (893 + 056 + 3 + 4 + 7)^3 \\
 &:= (8 + 9 + 305 + 634 + 7)^3 \\
 \mathbf{893871739} &:= (8 + 9 + 3 - 8 + 7 - 1 + 7 + 3 - 9)^7 \\
 &:= (-8 + 9 + 3 + 8 + 7 - 1 + 7 + 3 - 9)^7 \\
 &:= (8 - 9 + 3 + 8 + 7 + 1 + 7 + 3 - 9)^7 \\
 &:= (8 + 9 + 3 + 8 - 7 - 1 - 7 - 3 + 9)^7 \\
 &:= (8 + 9 + 3 - 8 + 7 + 1 - 7 - 3 + 9)^7 \\
 &:= (-8 + 9 + 3 + 8 + 7 + 1 - 7 - 3 + 9)^7 \\
 &:= (8 + 9 + 3 - 8 - 7 + 1 + 7 - 3 + 9)^7 \\
 &:= (-8 + 9 + 3 + 8 - 7 + 1 + 7 - 3 + 9)^7 \\
 &:= (8 + 9 - 3 + 8 - 7 - 1 - 7 + 3 + 9)^7 \\
 &:= (8 + 9 - 3 - 8 + 7 + 1 - 7 + 3 + 9)^7 \\
 &:= (-8 + 9 - 3 + 8 + 7 + 1 - 7 + 3 + 9)^7 \\
 &:= (8 - 9 + 3 - 8 + 7 - 1 + 7 + 3 + 9)^7 \\
 &:= (-8 - 9 + 3 + 8 + 7 - 1 + 7 + 3 + 9)^7 \\
 &:= (8 + 9 - 3 - 8 - 7 + 1 + 7 + 3 + 9)^7 \\
 &:= (-8 + 9 - 3 + 8 - 7 + 1 + 7 + 3 + 9)^7 \\
 &:= (89 + 3 - 87 + 1 + 7 - 3 + 9)^7 \\
 &:= (-89 + 3 + 87 - 1 + 7 + 3 + 9)^7 \\
 &:= (89 - 3 - 87 + 1 + 7 + 3 + 9)^7 \\
 &:= (8 + 93 + 8 - 71 - 7 - 3 - 9)^7 \\
 &:= (-8 + 93 - 8 - 71 + 7 - 3 + 9)^7 \\
 &:= (8 + 93 + 8 - 7 - 1 - 73 - 9)^7 \\
 &:= (8 + 93 - 8 + 7 + 1 - 73 - 9)^7 \\
 &:= (-8 + 93 + 8 + 7 + 1 - 73 - 9)^7 \\
 &:= (-8 + 93 - 8 + 7 - 1 - 73 + 9)^7 \\
 &:= (8 - 9 - 38 + 71 - 7 + 3 - 9)^7 \\
 &:= (8 + 9 + 38 - 7 - 17 - 3 - 9)^7 \\
 &:= (-8 - 9 + 38 - 7 + 17 - 3 - 9)^7 \\
 &:= (8 - 9 + 38 - 7 - 17 - 3 + 9)^7 \\
 &:= (-8 + 9 - 38 - 7 - 1 + 73 - 9)^7 \\
 &:= (8 - 9 - 38 - 7 + 1 + 73 - 9)^7
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 &:= (-8 - 9 - 38 - 7 - 1 + 73 + 9)^7 \\
 &:= (8 + 9 - 38 + 7 + 1 - 7 + 39)^7 \\
 &:= (8 + 9 - 38 - 7 + 1 + 7 + 39)^7 \\
 &:= (8 + 9 + 3 - 8 + 71 - 73 + 9)^7 \\
 &:= (-8 + 9 + 3 + 8 + 71 - 73 + 9)^7 \\
 &:= (8 - 9 + 3 - 8 + 71 - 7 - 39)^7 \\
 &:= (-8 - 9 + 3 + 8 + 71 - 7 - 39)^7 \\
 &:= (8 - 9 - 3 + 8 - 7 - 17 + 39)^7 \\
 &:= (-8 + 9 - 3 - 8 + 7 - 17 + 39)^7 \\
 &:= (-89 + 38 + 71 - 7 - 3 + 9)^7 \\
 &:= (-89 + 38 + 7 - 1 + 73 - 9)^7 \\
 &:= (-89 - 3 + 8 + 71 - 7 + 39)^7 \\
 &:= (8 + 93 - 87 + 17 - 3 - 9)^7 \\
 &:= (-8 - 93 + 87 + 1 - 7 + 39)^7 \\
 \mathbf{895745041} &:= (89 + 5 - 7 + 45 + 041)^4 \\
 \mathbf{895841344} &:= (8 + 958 + 4 - 1 + 3 - 4 - 4)^3 \\
 &:= (8 + 958 - 4 - 1 + 3 + 4 - 4)^3 \\
 &:= (8 + 958 - 4 - 1 + 3 - 4 + 4)^3 \\
 &:= (-8 + 958 + 4 - 1 + 3 + 4 + 4)^3 \\
 &:= (895 + 8 + 4 + 13 + 44)^3 \\
 \mathbf{898632125} &:= (-8 + 986 - 3 - 2 - 1 - 2 - 5)^3 \\
 &:= (898 + 63 + 2 - 1 - 2 + 5)^3 \\
 &:= (898 + 63 - 2 - 1 + 2 + 5)^3 \\
 &:= (8 + 986 - 3 - 2 + 1 - 25)^3 \\
 &:= (898 + 63 - 21 + 25)^3 \\
 \mathbf{901428696} &:= (901 - 4 - 2 + 86 - 9 - 6)^3 \\
 &:= (901 - 4 - 2 + 8 + 69 - 6)^3 \\
 &:= (901 - 4 + 2 - 8 + 69 + 6)^3 \\
 &:= (90 - 1 + 4 - 2 + 869 + 6)^3 \\
 \mathbf{904231063} &:= (904 - 2 + 3 - 1 + 063)^3 \\
 &:= (904 + 2 - 3 + 1 + 063)^3 \\
 \mathbf{915498611} &:= (-9 + 1 - 5 - 4 + 986 + 1 + 1)^3 \\
 &:= (91 + 5 + 4 + 9 + 861 + 1)^3 \\
 \mathbf{916132832} &:= (9 + 1 + 6 + 1 + 32 + 8 + 3 + 2)^5 \\
 &:= (9 + 1 + 6 + 1 + 3 + 2 + 8 + 32)^5 \\
 &:= (91 + 6 + 1 - 3 - 28 - 3 - 2)^5 \\
 &:= (91 - 6 + 1 + 3 - 28 + 3 - 2)^5 \\
 &:= (9 + 16 + 1 + 3 + 28 + 3 + 2)^5
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 &:= (-9 - 16 + 1 + 3 + 2 + 83 - 2)^5 & &:= (9 + 37 + 8 + 90 + 6 + 25)^4 \\
 &:= (-9 - 16 + 1 + 3 - 2 + 83 + 2)^5 & &:= (-9 - 3 + 78 + 90 - 6 + 25)^4 \\
 &:= (9 + 1 + 6 + 13 + 28 + 3 + 2)^5 & &**938313739** := (938 + 31 - 3 + 7 - 3 + 9)^3 \\
 &:= (-9 - 1 + 6 - 13 - 2 + 83 - 2)^5 & &:= (938 - 3 + 1 + 37 - 3 + 9)^3 \\
 &:= (9 - 1 + 6 - 1 - 32 + 83 - 2)^5 & &:= (938 - 3 + 1 - 3 + 7 + 39)^3 \\
 &:= (9 + 1 - 6 + 1 - 3 + 28 + 32)^5 & &**941192000** := (941 + 19 + 20 + 00)^3 \\
 &:= (-9 + 1 + 6 + 1 + 3 + 28 + 32)^5 & &**946966168** := (946 + 9 + 6 + 6 + 1 + 6 + 8)^3 \\
 &:= (91 - 61 + 3 + 28 + 3 - 2)^5 & &:= (9 + 4 + 6 + 966 - 1 + 6 - 8)^3 \\
 &:= (91 + 61 - 3 - 2 - 83 - 2)^5 & &:= (-9 + 4 + 6 + 966 + 1 + 6 + 8)^3 \\
 &:= (91 + 6 - 13 + 2 + 8 - 32)^5 & &**958585256** := (958 - 5 - 8 + 52 - 5 - 6)^3 \\
 &:= (-9 + 161 - 3 - 2 - 83 - 2)^5 & &**961310025** := (-9 + 6 + 1 + 31002 + 5)^2 \\
 &:= (-9 + 16 + 13 + 2 + 8 + 32)^5 & &**964430272** := (964 - 4 + 3 + 027 - 2)^3 \\
 &:= (-9 + 16 - 1 + 32 - 8 + 32)^5 & &**967361669** := (967 + 3 + 6 + 16 + 6 - 9)^3 \\
 &:= (9 + 1 - 61 + 32 + 83 - 2)^5 & &:= (967 - 3 + 6 + 16 - 6 + 9)^3 \\
 &:= (9 - 1 + 61 - 3 + 28 - 32)^5 & &:= (967 - 3 - 6 + 16 + 6 + 9)^3 \\
 916636176 := (91 + 66 - 3 + 6 + 1 + 7 + 6)^4 & &:= (967 - 36 + 1 + 66 - 9)^3 \\
 &:= (91 + 6 + 6 - 3 + 61 + 7 + 6)^4 & &:= (96 + 736 + 166 - 9)^3 \\
 &:= (9 + 166 + 3 - 6 + 1 + 7 - 6)^4 & &**970299000** := (970 + 2 + 9 + 9 + 000)^3 \\
 &:= (-9 + 166 - 3 + 6 + 1 + 7 + 6)^4 & &:= (9 - 7 - 02 + 990 + 00)^3 \\
 &:= (-9 + 16 - 6 + 3 - 6 + 176)^4 & &:= (-9 + 7 + 02 + 990 + 00)^3 \\
 918330048 := (918 + 3 + 3 + 0048)^3 & &:= (970 + 29 - 9 + 000)^3 \\
 &:= (91 + 833 + 0048)^3 & &:= (97 + 02 - 9 + 900 + 0)^3 \\
 921167317 := (921 + 1 + 6 + 7 + 31 + 7)^3 & &:= (9 + 70 + 2 + 9 + 900 + 0)^3 \\
 &:= (921 - 1 + 67 + 3 - 17)^3 & &:= (-9 + 70 + 29 + 900 + 0)^3 \\
 929714176 := (9 - 2 + 971 - 4 + 1 + 7 - 6)^3 & &**973242271** := (973 + 2 + 4 + 2 + 2 + 7 + 1)^3 \\
 &:= (9 + 2 + 971 - 4 - 1 - 7 + 6)^3 & &:= (973 + 24 + 2 - 2 - 7 + 1)^3 \\
 &:= (-9 - 2 + 971 + 4 - 1 + 7 + 6)^3 & &:= (973 + 24 - 2 + 2 - 7 + 1)^3 \\
 932574833 := (932 + 57 - 4 - 8 + 3 - 3)^3 & &:= (973 - 2 + 4 + 22 - 7 + 1)^3 \\
 &:= (932 + 57 - 4 - 8 - 3 + 3)^3 & &:= (973 - 2 - 4 - 2 + 27 - 1)^3 \\
 &:= (93 - 2 + 57 - 4 + 833)^3 & &:= (973 + 2 + 42 - 27 + 1)^3 \\
 935441352 := (935 + 44 - 1 - 3 + 5 - 2)^3 & &**976191488** := (976 + 19 + 1 - 4 + 8 - 8)^3 \\
 &:= (935 + 44 - 1 + 3 - 5 + 2)^3 & &:= (976 + 19 + 1 - 4 - 8 + 8)^3 \\
 &:= (935 - 4 + 41 + 3 + 5 - 2)^3 & &**979146657** := (979 + 14 + 6 + 6 - 5 - 7)^3 \\
 937890625 := (93 + 78 - 9 + 06 + 2 + 5)^4 & &:= (979 + 14 - 6 - 6 + 5 + 7)^3 \\
 &:= (93 - 7 + 8 + 90 - 6 + 2 - 5)^4 & &:= (979 + 1 + 4 + 66 - 57)^3 \\
 &:= (9 - 3 + 78 + 90 - 6 + 2 + 5)^4 & &**981506241** := (9 + 81 + 50 - 6 + 2 + 41)^4 \\
 &:= (-9 + 3 + 78 + 90 + 6 + 2 + 5)^4 & &**982107784** := (982 + 10 + 7 + 7 - 8 - 4)^3 \\
 &:= (9 + 3 + 7 + 89 + 062 + 5)^4 & &:= (-9 + 8 + 2 + 1077 - 84)^3
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 \mathbf{988047936} &:= (-9 - 8 + 80 + 4 - 7 + 936)^3 &:= (99 + 2 - 4 - 36 - 5 + 4 + 3)^5 \\
 &:= (98 + 804 + 7 + 93 - 6)^3 &:= (99 + 2 + 4 + 3 + 6 - 54 + 3)^5 \\
 \mathbf{991026973} &:= (-9 + 910 + 2 - 6 + 97 + 3)^3 &:= (9 + 92 + 4 - 36 - 5 - 4 + 3)^5 \\
 &:= (9 + 910 + 2 - 6 + 9 + 73)^3 &:= (9 + 92 - 4 - 36 - 5 + 4 + 3)^5 \\
 &:= (9 + 9 + 10 + 2 - 6 + 973)^3 &:= (-9 + 92 + 4 - 36 + 5 + 4 + 3)^5 \\
 &:= (991 + 02 - 69 + 73)^3 &:= (9 + 92 + 4 + 3 + 6 - 54 + 3)^5 \\
 \mathbf{992436543} &:= (9 + 9 + 24 + 3 + 6 + 5 + 4 + 3)^5 &:= (9 + 9 - 24 + 3 + 65 + 4 - 3)^5 \\
 &:= (9 + 9 - 2 + 43 + 6 + 5 - 4 - 3)^5 &:= (9 + 9 - 24 - 3 + 65 + 4 + 3)^5 \\
 &:= (9 + 9 + 2 + 43 - 6 + 5 + 4 - 3)^5 &:= (9 - 9 + 24 - 3 - 6 + 5 + 43)^5 \\
 &:= (9 + 9 + 2 + 43 + 6 - 5 - 4 + 3)^5 &:= (-9 + 9 + 24 - 3 - 6 + 5 + 43)^5 \\
 &:= (9 - 9 + 2 + 43 + 6 + 5 + 4 + 3)^5 &:= (-9 - 9 + 24 + 3 + 6 + 5 + 43)^5 \\
 &:= (-9 + 9 + 2 + 43 + 6 + 5 + 4 + 3)^5 &:= (-9 - 9 - 2 - 4 + 36 + 54 - 3)^5 \\
 &:= (9 - 9 - 2 + 4 + 3 + 65 - 4 - 3)^5 &:= (99 + 24 + 3 - 6 - 54 - 3)^5 \\
 &:= (-9 + 9 - 2 + 4 + 3 + 65 - 4 - 3)^5 &:= (99 + 24 - 3 - 6 - 54 + 3)^5 \\
 &:= (9 - 9 - 2 - 4 + 3 + 65 + 4 - 3)^5 &:= (-9 + 92 + 43 - 6 - 54 - 3)^5 \\
 &:= (-9 + 9 - 2 - 4 + 3 + 65 + 4 - 3)^5 &:= (9 - 9 - 24 + 36 + 54 - 3)^5 \\
 &:= (9 - 9 - 2 + 4 - 3 + 65 - 4 + 3)^5 &:= (-9 + 9 - 24 + 36 + 54 - 3)^5 \\
 &:= (-9 + 9 - 2 + 4 - 3 + 65 - 4 + 3)^5 &:= (9 + 9 + 24 - 36 + 54 + 3)^5 \\
 &:= (9 - 9 - 2 - 4 - 3 + 65 + 4 + 3)^5 &:= (-9 - 9 - 24 - 3 + 65 + 43)^5 \\
 &:= (-9 + 9 - 2 - 4 - 3 + 65 + 4 + 3)^5 &:= (9 - 9 - 2 + 43 + 65 - 43)^5 \\
 &:= (-9 - 9 + 2 + 4 + 3 + 65 + 4 + 3)^5 &:= (-9 + 9 - 2 + 43 + 65 - 43)^5 \\
 &:= (9 + 9 + 2 - 4 + 3 + 6 - 5 + 43)^5 &:= (9 - 9 - 2 - 43 + 65 + 43)^5 \\
 &:= (9 + 9 + 2 + 4 - 3 - 6 + 5 + 43)^5 &:= (-9 + 9 - 2 - 43 + 65 + 43)^5 \\
 &:= (9 + 9 - 2 - 4 - 3 + 6 + 5 + 43)^5 &:= (99 - 24 + 36 - 5 - 43)^5 \\
 &:= (9 - 9 + 2 + 4 + 3 + 6 + 5 + 43)^5 & \\
 &:= (-9 + 9 + 2 + 4 + 3 + 6 + 5 + 43)^5 & \\
 &:= (99 - 2 + 4 - 36 + 5 - 4 - 3)^5 & \\
 &:= (99 - 2 - 4 - 36 + 5 + 4 - 3)^5 & \\
 &:= (99 + 2 + 4 - 36 - 5 - 4 + 3)^5 &
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 \mathbf{994011992} &:= (994 + 01 + 1 + 9 - 9 + 2)^3 \\
 &:= (994 + 01 + 1 - 9 + 9 + 2)^3 \\
 &:= (9 - 9 + 4 + 01 + 1 + 992)^3 \\
 &:= (-9 + 9 + 4 + 01 + 1 + 992)^3
 \end{aligned}$$

7.9 10-Digits Semi-Selfie Numbers

$$\begin{aligned}
 \mathbf{100000000} &:= (10 + 0000 + 0000)^9 &:= (100 - 3 - 8 - 7 + 5 + 85 + 6)^4 \\
 &:= (1000 + 000000)^3 &:= (10 - 03 + 87 + 5 + 85 - 6)^4 \\
 \mathbf{1003003001} &:= (1003 - 003 + 001)^3 &:= (1 + 0038 + 75 + 8 + 56)^4 \\
 \mathbf{1003875856} &:= (1 + 003 + 8 + 75 + 85 + 6)^4 &:= (100 + 38 - 7 + 58 - 5 - 6)^4 \\
 &:= (100 + 3 + 87 - 5 - 8 - 5 + 6)^4 & \\
 &:= (100 + 3 + 8 - 7 - 5 + 85 - 6)^4 & \\
 \mathbf{1006012008} &:= (1006 - 012 + 008)^3 & \\
 \mathbf{1012048064} &:= (-1 - 01 + 204 + 806 - 4)^3 &
 \end{aligned}$$

$$1015075125 := (1015 - 07 + 5 - 1 - 2 - 5)^3$$

$$:= (1015 - 07 - 5 - 1 - 2 + 5)^3$$

$$:= (-10 + 1 + 507 + 512 - 5)^3$$

$$1018108216 := (1018 + 1 - 08 + 2 - 1 - 6)^3$$

$$:= (1018 - 1 - 08 + 2 + 1 - 6)^3$$

$$:= (1018 + 10 - 8 + 2 - 16)^3$$

$$:= (10 + 181 + 0821 - 6)^3$$

$$1021147343 := (1021 - 1 + 4 - 7 - 3 - 4 - 3)^3$$

$$:= (1021 + 1 - 4 - 7 + 3 - 4 - 3)^3$$

$$:= (1021 - 1 - 4 - 7 - 3 + 4 - 3)^3$$

$$:= (1021 + 1 - 4 - 7 - 3 - 4 + 3)^3$$

$$1024192512 := (1024 - 1 - 9 + 2 - 5 - 1 - 2)^3$$

$$:= (1024 + 1 - 9 - 2 - 5 + 1 - 2)^3$$

$$:= (1024 - 1 - 9 - 2 - 5 - 1 + 2)^3$$

$$:= (1024 + 1 + 9 - 25 + 1 - 2)^3$$

$$:= (1024 - 1 + 9 - 25 - 1 + 2)^3$$

$$1024320025 := (10 + 2 - 4 + 32002 - 5)^2$$

$$1026625681 := (102 + 6 + 6 + 2 + 56 + 8 - 1)^4$$

$$:= (-1 + 026 + 62 + 5 + 6 + 81)^4$$

$$:= (-1 + 02 + 66 + 25 + 6 + 81)^4$$

$$:= (-10 + 2 + 6 + 6 + 256 - 81)^4$$

$$1027243729 := (1 + 0272 + 4 + 3 + 729)^3$$

$$:= (1027 + 2 + 43 - 72 + 9)^3$$

$$:= (10 + 27 + 243 + 729)^3$$

$$1030301000 := (10 + 3 - 03 + 01000)^3$$

$$:= (10 - 3 + 03 + 01000)^3$$

$$:= (1030 - 30 + 10 + 00)^3$$

$$:= (10 + 30 - 30 + 1000)^3$$

$$:= (10 - 30 + 30 + 1000)^3$$

$$1032208384 := (1 + 032208 + 3 - 84)^2$$

$$1036433728 := (1036 - 4 - 33 + 7 - 2 + 8)^3$$

$$:= (1036 + 4 + 3 - 37 - 2 + 8)^3$$

$$:= (1036 + 43 - 3 - 72 + 8)^3$$

$$1039509197 := (1039 - 50 + 9 - 1 + 9 + 7)^3$$

$$:= (1039 - 5 - 09 - 19 + 7)^3$$

$$1042590744 := (104 - 2 + 5 + 907 + 4 - 4)^3$$

$$:= (104 - 2 + 5 + 907 - 4 + 4)^3$$

$$1045678375 := (1045 - 6 - 7 - 8 + 3 - 7 - 5)^3$$

$$:= (1045 + 6 - 78 + 37 + 5)^3$$

$$1048772096 := (104 + 877 + 20 + 9 + 6)^3$$

$$1049760000 := (104 + 9 + 7 + 60 + 000)^4$$

$$1051871913 := (105 - 1 + 8 - 7 - 1 + 913)^3$$

$$:= (105 + 1 - 8 + 7 - 1 + 913)^3$$

$$:= (105 - 1 - 8 + 7 + 1 + 913)^3$$

$$:= (10 + 5 + 1 + 87 + 1 + 913)^3$$

$$:= (1 + 051 + 871 + 91 + 3)^3$$

$$:= (-10 + 51 - 8 + 71 + 913)^3$$

$$:= (10 + 5 + 18 + 71 + 913)^3$$

$$1054977832 := (1054 - 9 - 7 - 7 - 8 - 3 - 2)^3$$

$$:= (-10 + 54 + 977 - 8 + 3 + 2)^3$$

$$:= (10 - 5 - 4 + 977 + 8 + 32)^3$$

$$:= (10 - 54 + 977 + 83 + 2)^3$$

$$1058089859 := (1058 - 08 - 9 - 8 - 5 - 9)^3$$

$$1067462648 := (10 - 6 + 746 + 264 + 8)^3$$

$$1073283121 := (107 - 3 - 2 + 83 - 1 - 2 - 1)^4$$

$$:= (1 + 073 + 2 + 83 + 1 + 21)^4$$

$$:= (107 + 32 + 8 + 31 + 2 + 1)^4$$

$$:= (-107 + 3 + 283 + 1 + 2 - 1)^4$$

$$:= (-107 + 3 + 283 - 1 + 2 + 1)^4$$

$$:= (10 + 73 + 2 + 83 + 12 + 1)^4$$

$$:= (-10 + 73 + 2 - 8 + 3 + 121)^4$$

$$:= (10 + 7 + 32 + 8 + 3 + 121)^4$$

$$:= (-107 + 3 - 28 + 312 + 1)^4$$

$$1073741824 := (10 + 7 - 3 + 7 - 4 - 1 - 8 - 2 - 4)^{30}$$

$$:= (10 + 7 + 3 + 7 - 4 - 1 - 8 - 2 - 4)^{10}$$

$$:= (10 + 7 + 3 - 7 + 4 - 1 - 8 - 2 - 4)^{30}$$

$$:= (10 - 7 + 3 + 7 + 4 - 1 - 8 - 2 - 4)^{30}$$

$$:= (10 + 7 - 3 + 7 - 4 + 1 - 8 - 2 - 4)^{15}$$

$$:= (10 + 7 + 3 - 7 + 4 + 1 - 8 - 2 - 4)^{15}$$

$$:= (10 - 7 + 3 + 7 + 4 + 1 - 8 - 2 - 4)^{15}$$

$$:= (10 + 7 - 3 - 7 - 4 - 1 + 8 - 2 - 4)^{15}$$

$$:= (10 - 7 - 3 + 7 - 4 - 1 + 8 - 2 - 4)^{15}$$

$$:= (-10 + 7 + 3 + 7 - 4 - 1 + 8 - 2 - 4)^{15}$$

$$:= (10 - 7 + 3 - 7 + 4 - 1 + 8 - 2 - 4)^{15}$$

$$:= (10 + 7 + 3 + 7 + 4 - 1 + 8 - 2 - 4)^6$$

$$:= (-10 + 7 - 3 + 7 + 4 + 1 + 8 - 2 - 4)^{10}$$

$$\begin{aligned} &:= (10+7-3+7-4+1-8+2-4)^{10} &:= (-10+7+3+7+4-1-8+2+4)^{10} \\ &:= (10+7-3-7+4+1-8+2-4)^{30} &:= (10+7-3-7-4+1-8+2+4)^{30} \\ &:= (10+7+3-7+4+1-8+2-4)^{10} &:= (10+7+3-7-4+1-8+2+4)^{10} \\ &:= (10-7-3+7+4+1-8+2-4)^{30} &:= (10-7-3+7-4+1-8+2+4)^{30} \\ &:= (10-7+3+7+4+1-8+2-4)^{10} &:= (10-7+3+7-4+1-8+2+4)^{10} \\ &:= (-10+7+3+7+4+1-8+2-4)^{30} &:= (-10+7+3+7-4+1-8+2+4)^{30} \\ &:= (10+7-3-7-4-1+8+2-4)^{10} &:= (10-7+3-7+4+1-8+2+4)^{30} \\ &:= (10-7-3+7-4-1+8+2-4)^{10} &:= (-10+7-3+7+4+1-8+2+4)^{15} \\ &:= (-10+7-3+7-4-1+8+2-4)^{30} &:= (10-7-3-7-4-1+8+2+4)^{30} \\ &:= (-10+7+3+7-4-1+8+2-4)^{10} &:= (10-7+3-7-4-1+8+2+4)^{10} \\ &:= (10-7-3-7+4-1+8+2-4)^{30} &:= (-10+7+3-7-4-1+8+2+4)^{30} \\ &:= (10-7+3-7+4-1+8+2-4)^{10} &:= (-10-7+3+7-4-1+8+2+4)^{30} \\ &:= (-10+7+3-7+4-1+8+2-4)^{30} &:= (-10+7-3-7+4-1+8+2+4)^{15} \\ &:= (-10-7+3+7+4-1+8+2-4)^{30} &:= (-10-7-3+7+4-1+8+2+4)^{15} \\ &:= (10-7+3-7-4+1+8+2-4)^{30} &:= (10-7-3-7-4+1+8+2+4)^{15} \\ &:= (-10+7-3+7-4+1+8+2-4)^{15} &:= (-10+7+3-7-4+1+8+2+4)^{15} \\ &:= (10-7-3-7+4+1+8+2-4)^{15} &:= (10+7-3+7-4+1+8+2+4)^6 \\ &:= (-10+7+3-7+4+1+8+2-4)^{15} &:= (-10-7+3+7-4+1+8+2+4)^{15} \\ &:= (10+7-3+7+4+1+8+2-4)^6 &:= (10+7+3-7+4+1+8+2+4)^6 \\ &:= (-10-7+3+7+4+1+8+2-4)^{15} &:= (10-7+3+7+4+1+8+2+4)^6 \\ &:= (10+7+3-7-4-1-8-2+4)^{30} &:= (1+073+7-4+1-8-2-4)^5 \\ &:= (10-7+3+7-4-1-8-2+4)^{30} &:= (1+073-7-4-1+8-2-4)^5 \\ &:= (10+7-3-7+4-1-8-2+4)^{15} &:= (-1+073-7-4+1+8-2-4)^5 \\ &:= (10-7-3+7+4-1-8-2+4)^{15} &:= (-1+073+7-4-1-8+2-4)^5 \\ &:= (-10+7+3+7+4-1-8-2+4)^{15} &:= (1+073-7+4-1-8-2+4)^5 \\ &:= (10+7+3-7-4+1-8-2+4)^{15} &:= (-1+073-7+4+1-8-2+4)^5 \\ &:= (10-7+3+7-4+1-8-2+4)^{15} &:= (-1+07+37+4-1-8-2-4)^6 \\ &:= (10-7+3-7-4-1+8-2+4)^{15} &:= (1+07+37-4+1-8+2-4)^6 \\ &:= (10+7+3+7-4-1+8-2+4)^6 &:= (1-07+37-4-1+8+2-4)^6 \\ &:= (-10+7-3+7-4+1+8-2+4)^{10} &:= (-1-07+37-4+1+8+2-4)^6 \\ &:= (10-7-3-7+4+1+8-2+4)^{10} &:= (-1+07+37-4-1-8-2+4)^6 \\ &:= (-10+7-3-7+4+1+8-2+4)^{30} &:= (1-07+37+4-1-8+2+4)^6 \\ &:= (-10+7+3-7+4+1+8-2+4)^{10} &:= (-1-07+37+4+1-8+2+4)^6 \\ &:= (-10-7-3+7+4+1+8-2+4)^{30} &:= (1+07+37+4+1+8+2+4)^5 \\ &:= (-10-7+3+7+4+1+8-2+4)^{10} &:= (1+07-3+74-1-8-2-4)^5 \\ &:= (10+7-3-7+4-1-8+2+4)^{10} &:= (-1+07-3+74+1-8-2-4)^5 \\ &:= (10-7-3+7+4-1-8+2+4)^{10} &:= (-1-07-3+74-1+8-2-4)^5 \\ &:= (-10+7-3+7+4-1-8+2+4)^{30} &:= (1-07+3+74-1-8-2+4)^5 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} &:= (-1-07+3+74+1-8-2+4)^5 & &:= (10+7-3+7+4-1+8-24)^{10} \\ &:= (1-07-3+74+1-8+2+4)^5 & &:= (10+7-3+7-4+1+8-24)^{30} \\ &:= (-1+07-3-7-4+18-2-4)^{15} & &:= (10+7+3+7-4+1+8-24)^{10} \\ &:= (-1-07-3+7-4+18-2-4)^{15} & &:= (10+7+3-7+4+1+8-24)^{30} \\ &:= (-1-07+3-7+4+18-2-4)^{15} & &:= (10-7+3+7+4+1+8-24)^{30} \\ &:= (-1+07+3+7+4+18-2-4)^6 & &:= (10-7-3-7-4-1-8+24)^{15} \\ &:= (1+07+3+7+4-18+2-4)^{30} & &:= (-10+7+3-7-4-1-8+24)^{15} \\ &:= (-1+07-3-7-4+18+2-4)^{10} & &:= (10+7-3+7-4-1-8+24)^6 \\ &:= (1-07+3-7-4+18+2-4)^{30} & &:= (-10-7+3+7-4-1-8+24)^{15} \\ &:= (-1-07-3+7-4+18+2-4)^{10} & &:= (10+7+3-7+4-1-8+24)^6 \\ &:= (-1-07-3-7+4+18+2-4)^{30} & &:= (10-7+3+7+4-1-8+24)^6 \\ &:= (1-07-3-7+4+18+2-4)^{15} & &:= (-10+7-3-7+4+1-8+24)^{10} \\ &:= (-1-07+3-7+4+18+2-4)^{10} & &:= (-10-7-3+7+4+1-8+24)^{10} \\ &:= (1+07-3+7+4+18+2-4)^6 & &:= (-10-7-3-7+4-1+8+24)^{10} \\ &:= (-1+07+3+7+4-18-2+4)^{15} & &:= (-10-7-3-7-4+1+8+24)^{30} \\ &:= (-1-07+3-7-4+18-2+4)^{15} & &:= (-10-7+3-7-4+1+8+24)^{10} \\ &:= (-1+07+3+7-4+18-2+4)^6 & &:= (10+7+3+7+4+1+8+24)^5 \\ &:= (1-07-3-7+4+18-2+4)^{10} & &:= (1+073-7-41+8+2-4)^6 \\ &:= (1+07+3+7-4-18+2+4)^{30} & &:= (-1+073+7-41-8-2+4)^6 \\ &:= (-1+07-3+7+4-18+2+4)^{30} & &:= (1-073+7-4-1+82-4)^{10} \\ &:= (1+07-3+7+4-18+2+4)^{15} & &:= (1-073-7+4-1+82-4)^{30} \\ &:= (-1+07+3+7+4-18+2+4)^{10} & &:= (-1-073+7-4+1+82-4)^{10} \\ &:= (-1-07-3-7-4+18+2+4)^{30} & &:= (-1-073-7+4+1+82-4)^{30} \\ &:= (1-07-3-7-4+18+2+4)^{15} & &:= (1-073-7+4+1+82-4)^{15} \\ &:= (-1-07+3-7-4+18+2+4)^{10} & &:= (-1+073+7+4-1-82+4)^{15} \\ &:= (1+07-3+7-4+18+2+4)^6 & &:= (1+073+7+4+1-82+4)^{10} \\ &:= (1+07+3-7+4+18+2+4)^6 & &:= (1-073-7-4-1+82+4)^{30} \\ &:= (1-07+3+7+4+18+2+4)^6 & &:= (-1-073-7+4-1+82+4)^{10} \\ &:= (10+7-3+7+41+8-2-4)^5 & &:= (-1-073-7-4+1+82+4)^{30} \\ &:= (-10-7-3-7+41-8+2-4)^{15} & &:= (1-073-7-4+1+82+4)^{15} \\ &:= (-10+7-3+7+41-8+2-4)^6 & &:= (1+073-7-4+1-8-24)^6 \\ &:= (-10-7-3-7+41-8-2+4)^{10} & &:= (-1+07+37-41+8-2-4)^{15} \\ &:= (10+7+3-7+41+8-2+4)^5 & &:= (1+07-37+41-8+2-4)^{30} \\ &:= (10-7+3+7+41+8-2+4)^5 & &:= (-1+07+37-41+8+2-4)^{10} \\ &:= (10-7-3-7+41-8+2+4)^6 & &:= (-1-07-37+41+8+2-4)^{30} \\ &:= (-10+7+3-7+41-8+2+4)^6 & &:= (1-07-37+41+8+2-4)^{15} \\ &:= (-10-7+3+7+41-8+2+4)^6 & &:= (-1+07-37+41-8-2+4)^{15} \\ &:= (-10-7-3-7+4+1+82+4)^5 & &:= (-1-07+37+41-8-2+4)^5 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} &:= (1 - 07 - 37 + 41 + 8 - 2 + 4)^{10} &:= (-1 + 07 + 3 - 7 - 4 - 18 + 24)^{15} \\ &:= (1 + 07 + 37 - 41 - 8 + 2 + 4)^{30} &:= (-1 - 07 + 3 + 7 - 4 - 18 + 24)^{15} \\ &:= (-1 + 07 - 37 + 41 - 8 + 2 + 4)^{10} &:= (1 + 07 - 3 - 7 + 4 - 18 + 24)^{10} \\ &:= (-1 - 07 + 37 - 41 + 8 + 2 + 4)^{30} &:= (1 - 07 - 3 + 7 + 4 - 18 + 24)^{10} \\ &:= (1 - 07 + 37 - 41 + 8 + 2 + 4)^{15} &:= (1 + 07 + 3 + 7 + 4 + 18 + 24)^5 \\ &:= (1 - 07 - 37 - 4 + 1 + 82 - 4)^6 &:= (107 + 3 - 7 - 41 + 8 - 2 - 4)^5 \\ &:= (1 + 07 + 37 - 4 - 1 - 8 - 24)^{10} &:= (107 - 3 + 7 - 41 - 8 - 2 + 4)^5 \\ &:= (1 - 07 + 37 + 4 - 1 - 8 - 24)^{30} &:= (107 - 3 - 7 - 4 + 1 - 82 - 4)^{10} \\ &:= (-1 + 07 + 37 - 4 + 1 - 8 - 24)^{10} &:= (10 - 73 + 74 + 1 - 8 + 2 - 4)^{30} \\ &:= (-1 - 07 + 37 + 4 + 1 - 8 - 24)^{30} &:= (10 + 73 - 74 - 1 - 8 - 2 + 4)^{30} \\ &:= (1 - 07 + 37 + 4 + 1 - 8 - 24)^{15} &:= (10 - 73 + 74 - 1 - 8 - 2 + 4)^{15} \\ &:= (-1 - 07 + 37 - 4 - 1 + 8 - 24)^{10} &:= (10 + 73 - 74 + 1 - 8 - 2 + 4)^{15} \\ &:= (1 + 07 + 37 + 4 - 1 + 8 - 24)^6 &:= (-10 - 73 + 74 + 1 + 8 - 2 + 4)^{30} \\ &:= (-1 + 07 + 37 + 4 + 1 + 8 - 24)^6 &:= (10 - 73 + 74 - 1 - 8 + 2 + 4)^{10} \\ &:= (1 + 07 + 37 + 4 - 1 - 8 + 24)^5 &:= (10 + 73 - 74 + 1 - 8 + 2 + 4)^{10} \\ &:= (-1 + 07 + 37 + 4 + 1 - 8 + 24)^5 &:= (-10 + 73 - 74 - 1 + 8 + 2 + 4)^{30} \\ &:= (-1 + 07 - 37 + 4 - 1 + 8 + 24)^{15} &:= (-10 - 73 + 74 - 1 + 8 + 2 + 4)^{15} \\ &:= (-1 - 07 + 37 + 4 - 1 + 8 + 24)^5 &:= (-10 + 73 - 74 + 1 + 8 + 2 + 4)^{15} \\ &:= (1 + 07 - 37 + 4 + 1 + 8 + 24)^{10} &:= (-10 + 73 - 7 - 4 + 18 - 2 - 4)^5 \\ &:= (1 + 07 - 3 - 74 - 1 + 82 - 4)^{10} &:= (-10 + 73 - 7 - 4 - 18 + 2 - 4)^6 \\ &:= (-1 + 07 - 3 - 74 + 1 + 82 - 4)^{10} &:= (10 + 73 - 7 + 4 - 18 - 2 + 4)^5 \\ &:= (1 - 07 + 3 - 74 + 1 + 82 - 4)^{30} &:= (-10 - 7 + 37 + 4 - 18 + 2 - 4)^{15} \\ &:= (-1 + 07 + 3 + 74 - 1 - 82 + 4)^{15} &:= (-10 - 7 + 37 - 4 + 18 + 2 - 4)^6 \\ &:= (1 + 07 - 3 + 74 + 1 - 82 + 4)^{30} &:= (-10 - 7 + 37 + 4 - 18 - 2 + 4)^{10} \\ &:= (1 + 07 + 3 + 74 + 1 - 82 + 4)^{10} &:= (10 + 7 - 37 + 4 + 18 - 2 + 4)^{15} \\ &:= (1 - 07 - 3 - 74 - 1 + 82 + 4)^{30} &:= (10 - 7 + 37 + 4 + 18 - 2 + 4)^5 \\ &:= (1 - 07 + 3 - 74 - 1 + 82 + 4)^{10} &:= (-10 - 7 + 37 - 4 - 18 + 2 + 4)^{15} \\ &:= (-1 - 07 - 3 - 74 + 1 + 82 + 4)^{30} &:= (10 - 7 + 37 + 4 - 18 + 2 + 4)^6 \\ &:= (1 - 07 - 3 - 74 + 1 + 82 + 4)^{15} &:= (10 + 7 - 37 + 4 + 18 + 2 + 4)^{10} \\ &:= (-1 - 07 + 3 - 74 + 1 + 82 + 4)^{10} &:= (10 + 7 - 3 + 74 - 18 - 2 - 4)^5 \\ &:= (1 - 07 - 3 + 74 - 1 - 8 - 24)^6 &:= (10 - 7 + 3 + 74 - 18 - 2 + 4)^5 \\ &:= (-1 - 07 - 3 + 74 + 1 - 8 - 24)^6 &:= (10 + 7 + 3 + 7 - 41 + 82 - 4)^5 \\ &:= (1 + 07 - 3 + 74 + 1 + 8 - 24)^5 &:= (-10 + 7 - 3 - 7 - 41 + 82 + 4)^6 \\ &:= (1 + 07 - 3 + 7 - 4 + 18 - 24)^{30} &:= (-10 - 7 - 3 + 7 - 41 + 82 + 4)^6 \\ &:= (1 + 07 + 3 + 7 - 4 + 18 - 24)^{10} &:= (10 - 7 - 3 - 7 + 41 - 8 - 24)^{30} \\ &:= (1 + 07 + 3 - 7 + 4 + 18 - 24)^{30} &:= (10 - 7 + 3 - 7 + 41 - 8 - 24)^{10} \\ &:= (-1 + 07 - 3 + 7 + 4 + 18 - 24)^{10} &:= (-10 + 7 + 3 - 7 + 41 - 8 - 24)^{30} \\ &:= (1 - 07 + 3 + 7 + 4 + 18 - 24)^{30} &:= (-10 - 7 + 3 + 7 + 41 - 8 - 24)^{30} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 & := (10 + 7 - 3 - 7 + 41 + 8 - 24)^6 \\
 & := (-10 - 7 + 3 - 7 + 41 + 8 - 24)^{15} \\
 & := (10 - 7 - 3 + 7 + 41 + 8 - 24)^6 \\
 & := (-10 + 7 + 3 + 7 + 41 + 8 - 24)^6 \\
 & := (10 + 7 + 3 + 7 - 41 - 8 + 24)^{30} \\
 & := (10 + 7 - 3 - 7 + 41 - 8 + 24)^5 \\
 & := (10 - 7 - 3 + 7 + 41 - 8 + 24)^5 \\
 & := (-10 + 7 + 3 + 7 + 41 - 8 + 24)^5 \\
 & := (10 + 7 + 3 - 7 - 41 + 8 + 24)^{15} \\
 & := (10 - 7 + 3 + 7 - 41 + 8 + 24)^{15} \\
 & := (1 + 073 + 7 - 41 - 8 - 24)^{10} \\
 & := (-1 + 073 - 7 - 41 + 8 - 24)^{10} \\
 & := (1 - 073 + 7 + 41 + 8 + 24)^{10} \\
 & := (1 + 07 - 37 - 41 + 82 - 4)^{10} \\
 & := (1 + 07 + 37 + 41 - 82 + 4)^{10} \\
 & := (1 - 07 - 37 - 41 + 82 + 4)^{30} \\
 & := (-1 - 07 + 37 - 41 - 8 + 24)^{15} \\
 & := (-107 - 3 - 7 + 41 + 82 - 4)^{30} \\
 & := (-107 + 3 - 7 + 41 + 82 - 4)^{10} \\
 & := (-10 + 73 - 74 - 1 - 8 + 24)^{15} \\
 & := (-10 - 73 + 74 + 1 - 8 + 24)^{10} \\
 & := (-10 + 73 + 7 + 4 - 18 - 24)^6 \\
 & := (10 + 7 + 37 - 4 - 18 - 24)^{10} \\
 & := (10 - 7 + 37 + 4 - 18 - 24)^{30} \\
 & := (-10 + 7 + 37 + 4 + 18 - 24)^6 \\
 & := (10 + 7 + 37 + 4 - 18 + 24)^5 \\
 & := (10 - 7 - 37 - 4 + 18 + 24)^{15} \\
 & := (10 - 7 - 3 + 74 - 18 - 24)^6 \\
 & := (-10 + 7 + 3 + 74 - 18 - 24)^6 \\
 & := (1 - 073 - 74 + 182 - 4)^6 \\
 & := (-1 + 073 - 74 - 18 + 24)^{15} \\
 & := (1 - 073 + 74 - 18 + 24)^{10} \\
 & := (107 - 37 + 4 - 18 - 24)^6 \\
 & := (-107 - 3 - 74 + 182 + 4)^{30} \\
 & := (-107 + 3 - 74 + 182 + 4)^{10} \\
 \mathbf{1076890625} & := (1076 + 8 - 90 + 6 + 25)^3 \\
 & := (10 + 76 + 8 + 906 + 25)^3 \\
 \mathbf{1080045576} & := (1080 + 04 + 5 - 57 - 6)^3 \\
 \mathbf{1083206683} & := (10 + 8 + 320 + 6 + 683)^3 \\
 \mathbf{1086373952} & := (1 + 08 + 63 + 7 - 3 + 952)^3 \\
 & := (1086 + 3 - 73 + 9 + 5 - 2)^3 \\
 & := (-1 + 0863 + 73 + 95 - 2)^3 \\
 & := (-10 + 8 + 637 + 395 - 2)^3 \\
 \mathbf{1089330025} & := (-1 + 08 - 9 + 33002 + 5)^2 \\
 \mathbf{1089547389} & := (-10 - 8 + 954 + 7 - 3 + 89)^3 \\
 & := (1 + 0895 + 47 - 3 + 89)^3 \\
 \mathbf{1095912791} & := (109 - 5 + 912 + 7 + 9 - 1)^3 \\
 \mathbf{1097199376} & := (1 + 097 + 1 + 99 - 3 - 7 - 6)^4 \\
 & := (1 + 097 - 1 - 9 + 93 + 7 - 6)^4 \\
 & := (-1 + 097 + 1 - 9 + 93 + 7 - 6)^4 \\
 & := (1 + 097 + 1 - 9 + 93 - 7 + 6)^4 \\
 & := (-1 + 09 + 71 + 99 + 3 + 7 - 6)^4 \\
 & := (1 + 09 + 71 + 99 + 3 - 7 + 6)^4 \\
 & := (-1 + 09 + 71 + 9 + 93 + 7 - 6)^4 \\
 & := (1 + 09 + 71 + 9 + 93 - 7 + 6)^4 \\
 & := (1 - 09 + 7 + 199 - 3 - 7 - 6)^4 \\
 & := (1 - 09 - 7 + 199 - 3 + 7 - 6)^4 \\
 & := (1 + 09 - 7 + 1 + 99 + 3 + 76)^4 \\
 & := (1 + 09 - 7 + 1 + 9 + 93 + 76)^4 \\
 & := (109 + 71 + 9 + 9 - 3 - 7 - 6)^4 \\
 & := (109 + 71 + 9 - 9 + 3 - 7 + 6)^4 \\
 & := (109 + 71 - 9 + 9 + 3 - 7 + 6)^4 \\
 & := (109 - 7 + 1 + 9 - 9 + 3 + 76)^4 \\
 & := (109 - 7 + 1 - 9 + 9 + 3 + 76)^4 \\
 & := (10 + 97 - 19 + 93 + 7 - 6)^4 \\
 & := (-10 - 9 + 71 + 99 + 37 - 6)^4 \\
 & := (10 + 9 + 7 + 199 - 37 - 6)^4 \\
 & := (10 - 9 - 7 + 19 + 93 + 76)^4 \\
 & := (1 - 097 + 199 + 3 + 76)^4 \\
 & := (1 - 097 + 1 - 99 + 376)^4 \\
 \mathbf{1099104768} & := (-1 + 09 - 9 + 1047 - 6 - 8)^3 \\
 & := (-1 - 09 + 9 + 1047 - 6 - 8)^3 \\
 & := (1 - 09 - 9 + 1047 - 6 + 8)^3 \\
 & := (109 + 910 + 4 + 7 - 6 + 8)^3 \\
 & := (1099 - 10 + 4 + 7 - 68)^3 \\
 \mathbf{1102302937} & := (-1 + 1023 - 02 + 9 - 3 + 7)^3
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 & := (-1 + 102 - 3 - 02 + 937)^3 \\
 & := (1102 - 30 - 29 - 3 - 7)^3 \\
 & := (1102 - 3 - 029 - 37)^3 \\
 \mathbf{1108717875} & := (1108 - 7 + 17 - 8 - 75)^3 \\
 & := (11 + 0871 + 78 + 75)^3 \\
 & := (1 + 10 + 871 + 78 + 75)^3 \\
 \mathbf{1111934656} & := (1111 - 9 - 3 - 4 - 65 + 6)^3 \\
 & := (1111 + 9 - 34 + 6 - 56)^3 \\
 & := (1 + 1119 - 34 + 6 - 56)^3 \\
 \mathbf{1115157653} & := (1115 + 1 + 5 - 76 - 5 - 3)^3 \\
 & := (1115 + 1 - 5 - 76 + 5 - 3)^3 \\
 \mathbf{1118386872} & := (1118 + 3 - 86 + 8 - 7 + 2)^3 \\
 & := (1118 + 3 + 8 - 6 - 87 + 2)^3 \\
 & := (-1 - 1 - 1 + 83 + 86 + 872)^3 \\
 \mathbf{1121513121} & := (1 + 1 + 2 + 151 + 31 - 2 - 1)^4 \\
 & := (1 + 1 - 2 + 151 + 31 + 2 - 1)^4 \\
 & := (-1 - 1 + 2 + 151 + 31 + 2 - 1)^4 \\
 & := (1 - 1 + 2 + 151 + 31 - 2 + 1)^4 \\
 & := (-1 + 1 + 2 + 151 + 31 - 2 + 1)^4 \\
 & := (1 - 1 - 2 + 151 + 31 + 2 + 1)^4 \\
 & := (-1 + 1 - 2 + 151 + 31 + 2 + 1)^4 \\
 & := (112 + 1 + 51 - 3 + 1 + 21)^4 \\
 & := (11 - 2 + 151 + 3 - 1 + 21)^4 \\
 & := (11 + 2 + 151 - 3 + 1 + 21)^4 \\
 & := (11 + 2 + 1 + 51 - 3 + 121)^4 \\
 & := (11 - 2 - 1 + 51 + 3 + 121)^4 \\
 & := (1 + 121 + 51 - 3 + 12 + 1)^4 \\
 & := (-1 - 121 - 5 - 1 + 312 - 1)^4 \\
 & := (1 + 12 + 151 - 3 + 1 + 21)^4 \\
 & := (1 + 12 + 1 + 51 - 3 + 121)^4 \\
 & := (-112 - 15 - 1 + 312 - 1)^4 \\
 & := (1 + 121 + 51 + 31 - 21)^4 \\
 \mathbf{1121622319} & := (1121 - 62 + 2 - 31 + 9)^3 \\
 & := (1121 - 62 + 2 - 3 - 19)^3 \\
 \mathbf{1133601561} & := (1 + 1 + 33601 + 5 + 61)^2 \\
 & := (11 + 33601 + 56 + 1)^2 \\
 \mathbf{1133668900} & := (11 + 33668 - 9 + 00)^2 \\
 \mathbf{1137893184} & := (11 + 3 + 7 + 8 + 931 + 84)^3 \\
 & := (1 + 137 + 893 + 1 + 8 + 4)^3 \\
 & := (1 + 13 + 7 + 8 + 931 + 84)^3 \\
 & := (1 - 1 + 37 - 8 + 931 + 84)^3 \\
 & := (-1 + 1 + 37 - 8 + 931 + 84)^3 \\
 \mathbf{1141166125} & := (11 + 411 + 6 + 612 + 5)^3 \\
 & := (-1 - 1 + 411 + 661 - 25)^3 \\
 & := (1 - 1 + 4 + 1166 - 125)^3 \\
 & := (-1 + 1 + 4 + 1166 - 125)^3 \\
 & := (-114 + 1166 - 12 + 5)^3 \\
 \mathbf{1146228736} & := (114 + 62 + 2 + 8 + 7 - 3 - 6)^4 \\
 & := (114 + 62 - 2 + 8 - 7 + 3 + 6)^4 \\
 & := (1 + 146 + 2 - 2 + 8 - 7 + 36)^4 \\
 & := (1 + 146 - 2 + 2 + 8 - 7 + 36)^4 \\
 & := (-1 + 146 + 2 + 2 - 8 + 7 + 36)^4 \\
 & := (-1 - 1 - 46 + 228 + 7 + 3 - 6)^4 \\
 & := (1 - 1 - 46 + 228 - 7 + 3 + 6)^4 \\
 & := (-1 + 1 - 46 + 228 - 7 + 3 + 6)^4 \\
 & := (-114 + 6 + 2 + 287 - 3 + 6)^4 \\
 & := (11 + 46 + 2 + 2 + 87 + 36)^4 \\
 & := (11 + 4 + 62 + 28 + 73 + 6)^4 \\
 & := (-11 + 4 + 6 + 228 - 7 - 36)^4 \\
 & := (1 + 146 - 22 - 8 + 73 - 6)^4 \\
 & := (1 + 146 - 2 - 28 + 73 - 6)^4 \\
 & := (1 + 14 + 62 + 28 + 73 + 6)^4 \\
 & := (1 - 1 + 462 - 287 + 3 + 6)^4 \\
 & := (-1 + 1 + 462 - 287 + 3 + 6)^4 \\
 & := (-11 + 46 + 228 - 73 - 6)^4 \\
 \mathbf{1151022592} & := (-1 + 15 + 1022 + 5 + 9 - 2)^3 \\
 \mathbf{1154320649} & := (1154 - 32 - 064 - 9)^3 \\
 \mathbf{1156340025} & := (-1 + 15 - 6 + 34002 - 5)^2 \\
 \mathbf{1160290625} & := (11 + 60 - 2 + 9 - 06 - 2 - 5)^5 \\
 & := (-11 + 60 - 2 + 9 + 06 - 2 + 5)^5 \\
 & := (11 + 60 + 2 - 9 - 06 + 2 + 5)^5 \\
 & := (11 - 6 + 02 - 9 + 062 + 5)^5 \\
 & := (-1 + 16 + 02 - 9 + 062 - 5)^5 \\
 & := (1 + 1 + 6 - 02 + 90 - 6 - 25)^5 \\
 & := (-1 - 1 + 6 + 02 + 90 - 6 - 25)^5 \\
 & := (1 + 1 - 6 - 02 + 90 + 6 - 25)^5
 \end{aligned}$$

	$:= (-1 - 1 - 6 + 02 + 90 + 6 - 25)^5$	$:= (1 + 16 + 2 - 2 - 6 + 1 + 4 - 6 - 7)^{19}$
	$:= (-11 + 60 + 29 - 06 - 2 - 5)^5$	$:= (1 + 16 - 2 + 2 - 6 + 1 + 4 - 6 - 7)^{19}$
	$:= (11 + 6 + 029 - 06 + 25)^5$	$:= (-1 + 16 + 2 - 2 - 6 - 1 - 4 + 6 - 7)^{19}$
	$:= (11 - 6 + 029 + 06 + 25)^5$	$:= (-1 + 16 - 2 + 2 - 6 - 1 - 4 + 6 - 7)^{19}$
	$:= (1 + 16 + 029 - 06 + 25)^5$	$:= (1 + 16 - 2 - 2 - 6 + 1 - 4 + 6 - 7)^{19}$
	$:= (1 + 1 - 60 + 2 + 90 + 6 + 25)^5$	$:= (1 + 16 - 2 - 2 - 6 - 1 - 4 - 6 + 7)^{19}$
	$:= (1 + 160 - 29 - 062 - 5)^5$	$:= (-1 + 16 - 2 - 2 - 6 + 1 - 4 - 6 + 7)^{19}$
	$:= (-1 - 1 + 602 + 90 - 625)^5$	$:= (1 - 16 + 2 + 2 + 6 - 1 - 4 + 6 + 7)^{19}$
1160935651	$:= (116 + 0935 + 6 - 5 - 1)^3$	$:= (-1 - 16 + 2 + 2 + 6 + 1 - 4 + 6 + 7)^{19}$
	$:= (116 + 0935 - 6 + 5 + 1)^3$	$:= (1 - 16 - 2 - 2 + 6 - 1 + 4 + 6 + 7)^{19}$
	$:= (11 + 60 + 935 - 6 + 51)^3$	$:= (-1 - 16 - 2 - 2 + 6 + 1 + 4 + 6 + 7)^{19}$
	$:= (1 + 160 + 935 + 6 - 51)^3$	$:= (1 + 1 + 6 + 2 - 2 - 6 + 14 - 6 - 7)^{19}$
1162261467	$:= (11 + 6 - 2 - 2 + 6 + 1 - 4 - 6 - 7)^{19}$	$:= (1 + 1 + 6 - 2 + 2 - 6 + 14 - 6 - 7)^{19}$
	$:= (11 + 6 + 2 - 2 - 6 + 1 + 4 - 6 - 7)^{19}$	$:= (-1 - 1 + 6 + 2 + 2 - 6 + 14 - 6 - 7)^{19}$
	$:= (11 + 6 - 2 + 2 - 6 + 1 + 4 - 6 - 7)^{19}$	$:= (1 + 1 - 6 + 2 - 2 + 6 + 14 - 6 - 7)^{19}$
	$:= (11 - 6 + 2 - 2 + 6 + 1 + 4 - 6 - 7)^{19}$	$:= (1 + 1 - 6 - 2 + 2 + 6 + 14 - 6 - 7)^{19}$
	$:= (11 - 6 - 2 + 2 + 6 + 1 + 4 - 6 - 7)^{19}$	$:= (-1 - 1 - 6 + 2 + 2 + 6 + 14 - 6 - 7)^{19}$
	$:= (11 + 6 - 2 - 2 - 6 + 1 - 4 + 6 - 7)^{19}$	$:= (1 + 1 + 6 + 2 + 2 + 6 - 14 + 6 - 7)^{19}$
	$:= (11 - 6 - 2 - 2 + 6 + 1 - 4 + 6 - 7)^{19}$	$:= (1 + 1 - 6 + 2 - 2 - 6 + 14 + 6 - 7)^{19}$
	$:= (-11 + 6 + 2 - 2 + 6 - 1 + 4 + 6 - 7)^{19}$	$:= (1 + 1 - 6 - 2 + 2 - 6 + 14 + 6 - 7)^{19}$
	$:= (-11 + 6 - 2 + 2 + 6 - 1 + 4 + 6 - 7)^{19}$	$:= (-1 - 1 - 6 + 2 + 2 - 6 + 14 + 6 - 7)^{19}$
	$:= (11 - 6 + 2 - 2 - 6 + 1 + 4 + 6 - 7)^{19}$	$:= (1 - 1 + 6 + 2 + 2 + 6 - 14 - 6 + 7)^{19}$
	$:= (11 - 6 - 2 + 2 - 6 + 1 + 4 + 6 - 7)^{19}$	$:= (-1 + 1 + 6 + 2 + 2 + 6 - 14 - 6 + 7)^{19}$
	$:= (11 + 6 - 2 - 2 - 6 - 1 - 4 - 6 + 7)^{19}$	$:= (1 - 1 - 6 + 2 - 2 - 6 + 14 - 6 + 7)^{19}$
	$:= (11 - 6 - 2 - 2 + 6 - 1 - 4 - 6 + 7)^{19}$	$:= (-1 + 1 - 6 + 2 - 2 - 6 + 14 - 6 + 7)^{19}$
	$:= (-11 + 6 + 2 + 2 + 6 + 1 - 4 - 6 + 7)^{19}$	$:= (1 - 1 - 6 - 2 + 2 - 6 + 14 - 6 + 7)^{19}$
	$:= (11 - 6 + 2 - 2 - 6 - 1 + 4 - 6 + 7)^{19}$	$:= (-1 + 1 - 6 - 2 + 2 - 6 + 14 - 6 + 7)^{19}$
	$:= (11 - 6 - 2 + 2 - 6 - 1 + 4 - 6 + 7)^{19}$	$:= (1 - 1 + 6 + 2 + 2 - 6 - 14 + 6 + 7)^{19}$
	$:= (-11 + 6 - 2 - 2 + 6 + 1 + 4 - 6 + 7)^{19}$	$:= (-1 + 1 + 6 + 2 + 2 - 6 - 14 + 6 + 7)^{19}$
	$:= (11 - 6 - 2 - 2 - 6 - 1 - 4 + 6 + 7)^{19}$	$:= (1 - 1 - 6 + 2 + 2 + 6 - 14 + 6 + 7)^{19}$
	$:= (-11 + 6 + 2 + 2 - 6 + 1 - 4 + 6 + 7)^{19}$	$:= (-1 + 1 - 6 + 2 + 2 + 6 - 14 + 6 + 7)^{19}$
	$:= (-11 - 6 + 2 + 2 + 6 + 1 - 4 + 6 + 7)^{19}$	$:= (11 - 6 + 22 - 6 - 1 - 4 - 6 - 7)^{19}$
	$:= (-11 + 6 - 2 - 2 - 6 + 1 + 4 + 6 + 7)^{19}$	$:= (-11 + 6 + 22 - 6 + 1 + 4 - 6 - 7)^{19}$
	$:= (-11 - 6 - 2 - 2 + 6 + 1 + 4 + 6 + 7)^{19}$	$:= (-11 - 6 + 22 + 6 + 1 + 4 - 6 - 7)^{19}$
	$:= (-1 + 16 + 2 - 2 + 6 - 1 - 4 - 6 - 7)^{19}$	$:= (11 + 6 - 22 + 6 - 1 + 4 + 6 - 7)^{19}$
	$:= (-1 + 16 - 2 + 2 + 6 - 1 - 4 - 6 - 7)^{19}$	$:= (-11 - 6 + 22 - 6 + 1 + 4 + 6 - 7)^{19}$
	$:= (1 + 16 - 2 - 2 + 6 + 1 - 4 - 6 - 7)^{19}$	$:= (-11 - 6 + 22 - 6 - 1 + 4 - 6 + 7)^{19}$
	$:= (-1 + 16 + 2 + 2 - 6 - 1 + 4 - 6 - 7)^{19}$	$:= (-11 + 6 - 2 + 26 + 1 - 4 - 6 - 7)^{19}$

$$\begin{aligned}
 \mathbf{1194389981} &:= (1 + 1 + 943 + 8 + 99 + 8 + 1)^3 \\
 &:= (1 + 1 + 943 + 8 + 9 + 98 + 1)^3 \\
 &:= (1 - 1 + 94 + 3 - 8 - 9 + 981)^3 \\
 &:= (-1 + 1 + 94 + 3 - 8 - 9 + 981)^3 \\
 &:= (1 + 1 + 9 + 43 + 8 + 998 + 1)^3 \\
 &:= (11 + 943 + 89 + 9 + 8 + 1)^3 \\
 &:= (11 + 943 + 8 + 9 + 9 + 81)^3 \\
 &:= (11 + 9 + 43 + 8 + 9 + 981)^3 \\
 &:= (11 + 9 + 4 + 38 + 998 + 1)^3 \\
 &:= (-11 + 9 - 4 - 3 + 89 + 981)^3 \\
 &:= (1 + 19 + 43 + 8 + 9 + 981)^3 \\
 &:= (1 + 19 + 4 + 38 + 998 + 1)^3
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 \mathbf{1196883216} &:= (1 + 1 + 96 + 88 + 3 + 2 + 1 - 6)^4 \\
 &:= (1 + 1 + 96 + 88 - 3 - 2 - 1 + 6)^4 \\
 &:= (-1 - 1 + 96 + 88 - 3 + 2 - 1 + 6)^4 \\
 &:= (1 - 1 + 96 + 88 - 3 - 2 + 1 + 6)^4 \\
 &:= (-1 + 1 + 96 + 88 - 3 - 2 + 1 + 6)^4 \\
 &:= (1 + 1 + 96 + 8 + 83 + 2 + 1 - 6)^4 \\
 &:= (-1 - 1 - 9 - 6 - 8 - 8 + 3 + 216)^4 \\
 &:= (1 + 196 + 8 + 8 - 32 - 1 + 6)^4 \\
 &:= (-1 + 196 + 8 + 8 - 32 + 1 + 6)^4 \\
 &:= (1 + 196 + 8 - 8 + 3 + 2 - 16)^4 \\
 &:= (1 + 196 - 8 + 8 + 3 + 2 - 16)^4 \\
 &:= (1 - 1 + 96 - 8 + 83 + 21 - 6)^4 \\
 &:= (-1 + 1 + 96 - 8 + 83 + 21 - 6)^4 \\
 &:= (119 + 6 + 88 - 32 - 1 + 6)^4 \\
 &:= (119 - 6 + 88 + 3 - 2 - 16)^4 \\
 &:= (119 - 6 + 8 + 83 - 2 - 16)^4 \\
 &:= (119 + 6 - 8 + 83 + 2 - 16)^4 \\
 &:= (-119 + 6 - 8 - 8 + 321 - 6)^4 \\
 &:= (-119 - 6 - 8 - 8 + 321 + 6)^4 \\
 &:= (11 + 9 + 68 + 83 + 21 - 6)^4 \\
 &:= (1 + 19 + 68 + 83 + 21 - 6)^4
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 \mathbf{1197770328} &:= (1 + 1 + 977 + 70 + 3 + 2 + 8)^3 \\
 \mathbf{1207949625} &:= (-1 - 2 + 07 + 94 + 962 + 5)^3 \\
 &:= (120 - 7 + 949 + 6 + 2 - 5)^3 \\
 &:= (120 - 7 - 9 + 4 + 962 - 5)^3 \\
 &:= (1 + 20 - 7 + 94 + 962 - 5)^3
 \end{aligned}$$

$$:= (1207 - 94 + 9 - 62 + 5)^3$$

$$\mathbf{1211355496} := (-12 + 1135 - 54 - 9 + 6)^3$$

$$\mathbf{1214767763} := (1214 - 7 - 67 - 76 + 3)^3$$

$$\mathbf{1218186432} := (1218 - 186 + 4 + 32)^3$$

$$\mathbf{1220703125} := (-1 + 2 + 2 + 07 + 03 - 1 - 2 - 5)^{13}$$

$$:= (1 + 2 - 2 + 07 + 03 + 1 - 2 - 5)^{13}$$

$$:= (1 - 2 + 2 + 07 + 03 + 1 - 2 - 5)^{13}$$

$$:= (1 + 2 + 2 + 07 - 03 - 1 + 2 - 5)^{13}$$

$$:= (-1 + 2 - 2 + 07 + 03 - 1 + 2 - 5)^{13}$$

$$:= (-1 - 2 + 2 + 07 + 03 - 1 + 2 - 5)^{13}$$

$$:= (-1 + 2 + 2 + 07 - 03 + 1 + 2 - 5)^{13}$$

$$:= (1 - 2 - 2 + 07 + 03 + 1 + 2 - 5)^{13}$$

$$:= (-1 + 2 - 2 + 07 - 03 - 1 - 2 + 5)^{13}$$

$$:= (-1 - 2 + 2 + 07 - 03 - 1 - 2 + 5)^{13}$$

$$:= (1 - 2 - 2 + 07 - 03 + 1 - 2 + 5)^{13}$$

$$:= (1 + 2 + 2 - 07 + 03 + 1 - 2 + 5)^{13}$$

$$:= (-1 - 2 - 2 + 07 - 03 - 1 + 2 + 5)^{13}$$

$$:= (-1 + 2 + 2 - 07 + 03 - 1 + 2 + 5)^{13}$$

$$:= (1 + 2 - 2 - 07 + 03 + 1 + 2 + 5)^{13}$$

$$:= (1 - 2 + 2 - 07 + 03 + 1 + 2 + 5)^{13}$$

$$:= (1 + 22 - 07 - 03 - 1 - 2 - 5)^{13}$$

$$:= (-1 + 22 - 07 - 03 + 1 - 2 - 5)^{13}$$

$$:= (1 + 2 + 20 - 7 - 03 - 1 - 2 - 5)^{13}$$

$$:= (-1 - 2 + 20 - 7 + 03 - 1 - 2 - 5)^{13}$$

$$:= (-1 + 2 + 20 - 7 - 03 + 1 - 2 - 5)^{13}$$

$$:= (1 - 2 + 20 - 7 - 03 - 1 + 2 - 5)^{13}$$

$$:= (-1 - 2 + 20 - 7 - 03 + 1 + 2 - 5)^{13}$$

$$:= (-1 + 22 + 07 + 03 - 1 - 25)^{13}$$

$$:= (-1 - 22 + 07 - 03 - 1 + 25)^{13}$$

$$:= (-1 + 2 + 20 + 7 + 03 - 1 - 25)^{13}$$

$$:= (1 - 2 + 20 + 7 + 03 + 1 - 25)^{13}$$

$$:= (-1 - 2 - 20 + 7 - 03 - 1 + 25)^{13}$$

$$:= (1 + 2 - 20 - 7 + 03 + 1 + 25)^{13}$$

$$:= (12 + 20 + 7 - 031 + 2 - 5)^{13}$$

$$:= (12 + 20 - 7 - 03 - 12 - 5)^{13}$$

$$:= (-12 + 20 - 7 - 03 + 12 - 5)^{13}$$

$$:= (-12 + 20 + 7 - 03 - 12 + 5)^{13}$$

$$:= (12 - 20 - 7 + 03 + 12 + 5)^{13}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 &:= (12 - 20 + 7 + 031 - 25)^{13} & &:= (1 + 2 - 4 - 9 + 198 + 3 + 3 - 6)^4 \\
 &:= (1 - 2 + 20 - 70 + 31 + 25)^{13} & &:= (1 + 2 - 4 - 9 + 198 - 3 - 3 + 6)^4 \\
 \mathbf{1221611509} &:= (1221 + 6 + 1 - 150 - 9)^3 & &:= (-1 - 2 - 4 - 9 + 198 + 3 - 3 + 6)^4 \\
 \mathbf{1222830961} &:= (1 + 2 + 2 + 2 + 83 + 096 + 1)^4 & &:= (-1 - 2 - 4 - 9 + 198 - 3 + 3 + 6)^4 \\
 &:= (122 - 2 + 83 - 09 - 6 - 1)^4 & &:= (124 + 9 - 1 + 9 + 8 + 33 + 6)^4 \\
 &:= (122 + 2 + 8 + 3 - 09 + 61)^4 & &:= (124 + 9 - 1 + 9 + 8 + 3 + 36)^4 \\
 &:= (1 + 222 - 8 - 30 + 9 - 6 - 1)^4 & &:= (12 - 4 + 91 + 9 + 83 + 3 - 6)^4 \\
 &:= (1 + 222 + 8 - 30 - 9 - 6 + 1)^4 & &:= (-1 - 24 + 9 + 198 + 3 - 3 + 6)^4 \\
 &:= (-1 + 222 - 8 - 30 + 9 - 6 + 1)^4 & &:= (-1 - 24 + 9 + 198 - 3 + 3 + 6)^4 \\
 &:= (1 + 2 + 228 - 30 - 9 - 6 + 1)^4 & &:= (1 + 2 + 49 - 1 + 98 + 33 + 6)^4 \\
 &:= (1 + 2 - 2 + 283 - 096 - 1)^4 & &:= (-1 + 2 + 49 + 1 + 98 + 33 + 6)^4 \\
 &:= (1 - 2 + 2 + 283 - 096 - 1)^4 & &:= (1 + 2 + 49 - 1 + 98 + 3 + 36)^4 \\
 &:= (-1 + 2 - 2 + 283 - 096 + 1)^4 & &:= (-1 + 2 + 49 + 1 + 98 + 3 + 36)^4 \\
 &:= (-1 - 2 + 2 + 283 - 096 + 1)^4 & &:= (124 + 9 - 19 + 83 - 3 - 6)^4 \\
 &:= (12 + 22 + 83 + 09 + 61)^4 & &:= (124 - 9 - 19 + 83 + 3 + 6)^4 \\
 &:= (1 - 2 + 228 + 30 - 9 - 61)^4 & &:= (124 + 9 - 1 + 9 + 83 - 36)^4 \\
 \mathbf{1225350025} &:= (-1 + 2 + 2 + 5 + 35002 - 5)^2 & &:= (12 + 49 - 1 + 9 + 83 + 36)^4 \\
 \mathbf{1225350025} &:= (-1 + 2 + 2 - 5 + 35002 + 5)^2 & &:= (12 - 4 + 9 + 198 - 33 + 6)^4 \\
 \mathbf{1235100736} &:= (-1 + 2 + 35100 + 7 + 36)^2 & &:= (-1 + 249 - 19 - 8 + 3 - 36)^4 \\
 \mathbf{1235171025} &:= (1 - 2 + 35171 - 025)^2 & &:= (-1 + 249 - 1 - 98 + 33 + 6)^4 \\
 \mathbf{1238833224} &:= (-1 + 238 + 833 + 2 - 2 + 4)^3 & &:= (-1 + 249 - 1 - 98 + 3 + 36)^4 \\
 &:= (-1 + 238 + 833 - 2 + 2 + 4)^3 & &:= (-1 + 2 + 49 + 19 + 83 + 36)^4 \\
 &:= (12 - 3 + 8 + 833 + 224)^3 & &:= (12 - 49 + 198 + 33 - 6)^4 \\
 \mathbf{1242296875} &:= (-12 + 42 + 2 + 968 + 75)^3 & &:= (-1 + 2 + 49 - 198 + 336)^4 \\
 &:= (1 - 24 + 229 - 6 + 875)^3 & & \\
 \mathbf{1245766976} &:= (124 - 5 - 7 - 6 - 6 + 976)^3 & & \\
 &:= (1 + 24 + 5 + 76 - 6 + 976)^3 & & \\
 &:= (-1 + 24 - 5 + 76 + 6 + 976)^3 & & \\
 &:= (1 - 24 + 57 + 66 + 976)^3 & & \\
 \mathbf{1249198336} &:= (-1 + 2 + 4 + 91 + 98 + 3 - 3 - 6)^4 & & \\
 &:= (-1 + 2 + 4 + 91 + 98 - 3 + 3 - 6)^4 & & \\
 &:= (1 + 2 - 4 + 91 + 98 + 3 + 3 - 6)^4 & & \\
 &:= (1 + 2 - 4 + 91 + 98 - 3 - 3 + 6)^4 & & \\
 &:= (-1 - 2 - 4 + 91 + 98 + 3 - 3 + 6)^4 & & \\
 &:= (-1 - 2 - 4 + 91 + 98 - 3 + 3 + 6)^4 & & \\
 &:= (-1 - 2 - 4 + 9 + 198 - 3 - 3 - 6)^4 & & \\
 &:= (-1 + 2 + 4 - 9 + 198 + 3 - 3 - 6)^4 & & \\
 &:= (-1 + 2 + 4 - 9 + 198 - 3 + 3 - 6)^4 & & \\
 & & & \mathbf{1249243533} := (124 + 924 + 35 - 3 - 3)^3 \\
 & & & \mathbf{1252332576} := (12 + 52 - 3 - 3 + 2 + 5 + 7 - 6)^5 \\
 & & &:= (12 + 52 + 3 + 3 + 2 - 5 - 7 + 6)^5 \\
 & & &:= (12 + 52 + 3 - 3 - 2 + 5 - 7 + 6)^5 \\
 & & &:= (12 + 52 - 3 + 3 - 2 + 5 - 7 + 6)^5 \\
 & & &:= (-12 + 52 + 3 + 3 + 2 + 5 + 7 + 6)^5 \\
 & & &:= (12 + 5 + 2 - 3 + 32 + 5 + 7 + 6)^5 \\
 & & &:= (12 + 5 + 2 - 3 - 3 + 2 + 57 - 6)^5 \\
 & & &:= (12 - 5 - 2 + 3 - 3 - 2 + 57 + 6)^5 \\
 & & &:= (12 - 5 - 2 - 3 + 3 - 2 + 57 + 6)^5 \\
 & & &:= (-12 + 5 + 2 + 3 + 3 + 2 + 57 + 6)^5 \\
 & & &:= (-12 + 5 - 2 + 3 + 3 - 2 - 5 + 76)^5 \\
 & & &:= (-12 - 5 - 2 + 3 + 3 - 2 + 5 + 76)^5 \\
 & & &:= (-1 + 25 + 23 + 3 - 2 + 5 + 7 + 6)^5
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 &:= (1 + 25 + 23 - 3 + 2 + 5 + 7 + 6)^5 & &:= (12 - 52 + 33 + 2 - 5 + 76)^5 \\
 &:= (1 + 25 + 2 + 3 - 3 + 25 + 7 + 6)^5 & &:= (12 - 52 + 3 + 32 - 5 + 76)^5 \\
 &:= (1 + 25 + 2 - 3 + 3 + 25 + 7 + 6)^5 & &:= (-1 + 25 + 23 - 32 + 57 - 6)^5 \\
 &:= (-1 + 25 - 2 + 3 + 3 + 25 + 7 + 6)^5 & &:= (1 - 25 - 23 + 32 + 5 + 76)^5 \\
 &:= (-1 + 2 + 52 + 33 - 2 - 5 - 7 - 6)^5 & &:= (12 - 523 + 3 - 2 + 576)^5 \\
 &:= (-1 - 2 + 52 + 33 + 2 - 5 - 7 - 6)^5 & & \mathbf{1252726552} := (1 + 2 + 527 + 2 - 6 + 552)^3 \\
 &:= (1 + 2 + 52 - 3 + 32 - 5 - 7 - 6)^5 & & \quad := (1252 - 726 + 552)^3 \\
 &:= (-1 - 2 + 52 + 3 + 32 - 5 - 7 - 6)^5 & & \mathbf{1256135364} := (12 + 5 + 61 + 35364)^2 \\
 &:= (1 + 2 + 5 + 23 - 3 + 25 + 7 + 6)^5 & & \mathbf{1256216039} := (1256 - 216 + 039)^3 \\
 &:= (-1 - 2 + 5 + 23 + 3 + 25 + 7 + 6)^5 & & \mathbf{1261599361} := (-1 + 26159 + 9361)^2 \\
 &:= (125 + 2 + 3 - 3 + 2 - 57 - 6)^5 & & \mathbf{1263214441} := (1 + 2 + 632 + 1 + 444 + 1)^3 \\
 &:= (125 + 2 - 3 + 3 + 2 - 57 - 6)^5 & & \quad := (1 + 2 + 632 + 1 + 4 + 441)^3 \\
 &:= (-12 + 52 + 3 - 3 + 25 + 7 - 6)^5 & & \mathbf{1266723368} := (1 + 2 - 6 - 6 + 723 + 368)^3 \\
 &:= (-12 + 52 - 3 + 3 + 25 + 7 - 6)^5 & & \mathbf{1270238787} := (-12 + 70 + 238 + 787)^3 \\
 &:= (12 + 5 + 23 + 32 - 5 - 7 + 6)^5 & & \mathbf{1273760704} := (-1 - 2 + 7 + 376 + 0704)^3 \\
 &:= (12 - 5 + 23 + 32 + 5 - 7 + 6)^5 & & \mathbf{1275989841} := (1 + 2 + 75 + 9 + 89 + 8 + 4 + 1)^4 \\
 &:= (-12 + 5 + 23 + 32 + 5 + 7 + 6)^5 & & \quad := (1 + 2 + 75 + 9 + 8 + 9 + 84 + 1)^4 \\
 &:= (-12 + 5 + 23 - 3 + 2 + 57 - 6)^5 & & \quad := (-1 - 2 + 7 - 5 + 98 + 9 + 84 - 1)^4 \\
 &:= (12 + 5 - 23 + 3 - 2 - 5 + 76)^5 & & \quad := (-1 + 2 - 7 + 5 + 98 + 9 + 84 - 1)^4 \\
 &:= (12 - 5 - 23 + 3 - 2 + 5 + 76)^5 & & \quad := (1 + 2 + 7 + 5 + 98 - 9 + 84 + 1)^4 \\
 &:= (12 - 5 + 2 + 33 + 25 - 7 + 6)^5 & & \quad := (1 - 2 - 7 + 5 + 98 + 9 + 84 + 1)^4 \\
 &:= (-12 + 5 + 2 + 33 + 25 + 7 + 6)^5 & & \quad := (127 - 5 - 9 + 89 - 8 - 4 - 1)^4 \\
 &:= (12 + 5 - 2 + 3 - 3 - 25 + 76)^5 & & \quad := (127 + 5 - 9 - 8 - 9 + 84 - 1)^4 \\
 &:= (12 + 5 - 2 - 3 + 3 - 25 + 76)^5 & & \quad := (127 + 5 + 9 + 8 - 9 + 8 + 41)^4 \\
 &:= (12 - 5 + 2 + 3 + 3 - 25 + 76)^5 & & \quad := (127 + 5 - 9 + 8 + 9 + 8 + 41)^4 \\
 &:= (-1 - 25 - 2 + 33 - 2 + 57 + 6)^5 & & \quad := (12 + 75 + 98 + 9 - 8 + 4 - 1)^4 \\
 &:= (-1 + 25 + 2 - 33 + 2 - 5 + 76)^5 & & \quad := (12 + 75 + 98 - 9 + 8 + 4 + 1)^4 \\
 &:= (1 - 25 - 2 - 3 + 32 + 57 + 6)^5 & & \quad := (12 + 75 + 9 - 8 + 98 + 4 - 1)^4 \\
 &:= (1 + 25 - 2 + 3 - 32 - 5 + 76)^5 & & \quad := (12 + 75 - 9 + 8 + 98 + 4 + 1)^4 \\
 &:= (-1 + 2 + 5 - 23 + 32 + 57 - 6)^5 & & \quad := (12 + 7 + 59 + 8 + 98 + 4 + 1)^4 \\
 &:= (1 - 2 - 5 - 23 + 32 + 57 + 6)^5 & & \quad := (-12 + 7 - 5 + 98 + 98 + 4 - 1)^4 \\
 &:= (1 - 2 + 5 + 23 - 32 - 5 + 76)^5 & & \quad := (12 + 7 + 5 - 9 + 89 + 84 + 1)^4 \\
 &:= (1 - 2 - 5 + 23 - 32 + 5 + 76)^5 & & \quad := (-1 + 275 + 9 - 89 - 8 + 4 - 1)^4 \\
 &:= (-1 + 2 - 5 + 2 - 33 + 25 + 76)^5 & & \quad := (1 + 275 - 9 - 89 + 8 + 4 - 1)^4 \\
 &:= (125 - 23 - 32 - 5 + 7 - 6)^5 & & \quad := (-1 + 275 - 9 - 89 + 8 + 4 + 1)^4 \\
 &:= (125 + 23 - 3 + 2 - 5 - 76)^5 & & \quad := (1 + 27 + 59 + 89 + 8 + 4 + 1)^4 \\
 &:= (125 - 2 - 33 - 25 + 7 - 6)^5 & & \quad := (1 + 27 + 59 + 8 + 9 + 84 + 1)^4 \\
 &:= (125 - 2 - 3 - 3 + 25 - 76)^5 & & \quad := (1 + 27 + 5 + 98 + 9 + 8 + 41)^4
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 &:= (1 + 27 + 5 + 9 + 8 + 98 + 41)^4 & &:= (-1 - 2 + 91 + 4 - 6 + 7 + 9 - 69)^6 \\
 &:= (-1 + 2 + 75 - 9 + 89 - 8 + 41)^4 & &:= (-1 + 2 - 9 - 14 + 67 - 9 + 6 - 9)^6 \\
 &:= (-1 + 2 + 7 + 59 + 89 - 8 + 41)^4 & &:= (-1 - 2 - 9 - 14 + 6 - 7 - 9 + 69)^6 \\
 &:= (1 - 2 - 7 + 59 + 89 + 8 + 41)^4 & &:= (-1 + 2 + 9 - 1 + 4 - 67 + 96 - 9)^6 \\
 \mathbf{1280000000} &:= (12 + 8 + 0000 + 000)^7 & &:= (1 - 2 + 9 + 1 + 4 - 67 + 96 - 9)^6 \\
 \mathbf{1287913472} &:= (12 + 87 + 913 + 4 + 72)^3 & &:= (-1 + 2 - 9 - 1 + 4 - 67 + 96 + 9)^6 \\
 \mathbf{1287913472} &:= (1 + 2 + 879 + 134 + 72)^3 & &:= (1 - 2 - 9 + 1 + 4 - 67 + 96 + 9)^6 \\
 \mathbf{1291467969} &:= (12 + 9 + 1 + 4 + 6 + 7 + 9 - 6 - 9)^6 & &:= (1 + 2 + 9 + 1 + 4 + 6 + 79 - 69)^6 \\
 &:= (12 + 9 + 1 + 4 - 6 + 7 + 9 + 6 - 9)^6 & &:= (129 - 1 - 4 - 67 - 9 - 6 - 9)^6 \\
 &:= (12 + 9 + 1 + 4 + 6 + 7 - 9 - 6 + 9)^6 & &:= (129 - 1 - 4 - 6 - 7 - 9 - 69)^6 \\
 &:= (12 - 9 + 1 + 4 + 6 + 7 + 9 - 6 + 9)^6 & &:= (12 + 91 + 4 + 6 + 7 - 96 + 9)^6 \\
 &:= (12 + 9 + 1 + 4 - 6 + 7 - 9 + 6 + 9)^6 & &:= (12 + 9 + 1 + 4 + 67 + 9 - 69)^6 \\
 &:= (12 - 9 + 1 + 4 - 6 + 7 + 9 + 6 + 9)^6 & &:= (1 - 29 + 14 - 6 - 7 - 9 + 69)^6 \\
 &:= (1 + 2 + 9 + 14 + 6 + 7 + 9 - 6 - 9)^6 & &:= (-1 - 29 - 14 + 6 - 7 + 9 + 69)^6 \\
 &:= (1 + 2 + 9 + 14 - 6 + 7 + 9 + 6 - 9)^6 & &:= (-1 + 2 - 91 - 4 + 67 - 9 + 69)^6 \\
 &:= (1 + 2 + 9 + 14 + 6 + 7 - 9 - 6 + 9)^6 & &:= (1 + 2 + 9 + 14 + 67 + 9 - 69)^6 \\
 &:= (1 - 2 + 9 + 14 + 6 - 7 + 9 - 6 + 9)^6 & &:= (1 - 2 + 9 + 14 - 67 + 9 + 69)^6 \\
 &:= (-1 - 2 + 9 + 14 - 6 + 7 + 9 - 6 + 9)^6 & &:= (129 - 14 - 6 - 79 - 6 + 9)^6 \\
 &:= (1 + 2 - 9 + 14 + 6 + 7 + 9 - 6 + 9)^6 & &:= (12 + 91 + 4 + 6 + 7 + 969)^3 \\
 &:= (1 + 2 + 9 + 14 - 6 + 7 - 9 + 6 + 9)^6 & &:= (12 - 9 + 14 + 6 + 79 - 69)^6 \\
 &:= (1 - 2 + 9 + 14 - 6 - 7 + 9 + 6 + 9)^6 & &:= (1 + 291 + 4 + 6 + 796 - 9)^3 \\
 &:= (1 + 2 - 9 + 14 - 6 + 7 + 9 + 6 + 9)^6 & &:= (1 - 29 + 146 - 7 - 9 - 69)^6 \\
 &:= (-1 + 2 + 9 - 14 + 6 + 7 + 9 + 6 + 9)^6 & &:= (1 + 29 + 14 + 67 - 9 - 69)^6 \\
 &:= (12 - 9 + 1 + 46 + 7 - 9 - 6 - 9)^6 & &:= (1 + 2 + 914 + 67 + 96 + 9)^3 \\
 &:= (-12 - 9 - 1 - 4 + 6 - 7 - 9 + 69)^6 & & \mathbf{1296360025} := (-1 + 2 - 9 + 6 + 36002 + 5)^2 \\
 &:= (1 + 29 + 14 + 6 + 7 - 9 - 6 - 9)^6 & & \mathbf{1298596571} := (1 - 2 + 985 + 96 + 5 + 7 - 1)^3 \\
 &:= (1 + 29 + 14 - 6 + 7 - 9 + 6 - 9)^6 & & &:= (-1 - 2 + 985 + 96 + 5 + 7 + 1)^3 \\
 &:= (-1 + 29 - 14 + 6 + 7 + 9 + 6 - 9)^6 & & &:= (129 + 8 - 5 + 965 - 7 + 1)^3 \\
 &:= (-1 + 29 - 14 + 6 + 7 - 9 + 6 + 9)^6 & & &:= (-1 - 29 + 85 + 965 + 71)^3 \\
 &:= (1 - 29 - 1 + 4 - 6 + 79 - 6 - 9)^6 & & \mathbf{1305015625} := (-1 + 30501 + 5625)^2 \\
 &:= (-1 - 29 + 1 + 4 - 6 + 79 - 6 - 9)^6 & & \mathbf{1311236521} := (-1 - 311 + 2 + 36521)^2 \\
 &:= (-1 + 2 + 91 - 46 - 7 + 9 - 6 - 9)^6 & & \mathbf{1312932375} := (13 - 1293 + 2375)^3 \\
 &:= (-1 + 2 + 91 - 46 - 7 - 9 - 6 + 9)^6 & & \mathbf{1313627536} := (1 + 3 + 1 + 36275 - 36)^2 \\
 &:= (1 - 2 + 91 + 4 - 67 + 9 + 6 - 9)^6 & & \mathbf{1316532736} := (13 - 1653 + 2736)^3 \\
 &:= (-1 + 2 + 91 - 4 - 67 + 9 - 6 + 9)^6 & & \mathbf{1323753192} := (1 + 323 + 753 + 19 + 2)^3 \\
 &:= (1 - 2 + 91 + 4 - 67 - 9 + 6 + 9)^6 & & \mathbf{1327436356} := (-1 + 3 + 2 + 74 + 36356)^2 \\
 &:= (1 + 2 + 91 + 4 + 6 + 7 - 9 - 69)^6 & & \mathbf{1330863361} := (133 + 086 - 33 + 6 - 1)^4 \\
 &:= (1 - 2 + 91 + 4 + 6 - 7 + 9 - 69)^6 & & &:= (1 + 3 + 308 - 63 + 3 - 61)^4
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 & := (133 + 086 + 33 - 61)^4 & & := (1 - 3 + 58 - 9 + 5 + 44 + 96)^4 \\
 \mathbf{1336487364} & := (1 + 3 + 36487 + 3 + 64)^2 & & := (135 - 89 + 54 - 4 + 96)^4 \\
 \mathbf{1336560481} & := (1 + 3 + 36560 + 4 - 8 - 1)^2 & & := (-13 + 58 + 95 - 44 + 96)^4 \\
 & := (-1 - 3 + 36560 - 4 + 8 - 1)^2 & & \mathbf{1359101956} := (1 + 35910 - 1 + 956)^2 \\
 & := (-1 + 3 + 36560 + 4 - 8 + 1)^2 & & := (-1 + 35910 + 1 + 956)^2 \\
 \mathbf{1336633600} & := (-13 + 36633 - 60 + 0)^2 & & \mathbf{1366633024} := (-1 + 36663 + 302 + 4)^2 \\
 \mathbf{1338273208} & := (-1 - 3 + 382 + 732 - 08)^3 & & \mathbf{1367631000} := (1 + 36 + 76 - 3 + 1000)^3 \\
 \mathbf{1349232625} & := (-13 + 492 + 3 - 2 + 625)^3 & & \mathbf{1369296016} := (-1 + 36929 + 60 + 16)^2 \\
 & := (1349 + 23 - 262 - 5)^3 & & \mathbf{1369370025} := (13 - 6 - 9 + 37002 + 5)^2 \\
 \mathbf{1350125107} & := (13 + 50 + 1 + 2 - 5 - 1 + 07)^5 & & \mathbf{1369518049} := (-1 + 36951 + 8 + 049)^2 \\
 & := (13 + 50 - 1 + 2 - 5 + 1 + 07)^5 & & \mathbf{1369962169} := (1 + 36996 + 2 - 1 + 6 + 9)^2 \\
 & := (13 - 5 - 01 + 2 + 51 + 07)^5 & & := (-1 + 36996 + 2 + 1 + 6 + 9)^2 \\
 & := (1 + 3 + 50 + 12 - 5 - 1 + 07)^5 & & := (-1 + 36996 + 21 + 6 - 9)^2 \\
 & := (-1 + 3 + 50 + 12 - 5 + 1 + 07)^5 & & \mathbf{1370036196} := (1 + 37003 + 6 + 1 + 9 - 6)^2 \\
 & := (1 + 3 + 50 - 1 + 2 - 5 + 10 + 7)^5 & & := (1 + 37003 - 6 + 1 + 9 + 6)^2 \\
 & := (-1 + 3 + 50 + 1 + 2 - 5 + 10 + 7)^5 & & \mathbf{1370110225} := (-1 + 37011 + 02 - 2 + 5)^2 \\
 & := (1 - 3 + 50 - 1 - 2 + 5 + 10 + 7)^5 & & := (-1 + 37011 - 02 + 2 + 5)^2 \\
 & := (-1 - 3 + 50 + 1 - 2 + 5 + 10 + 7)^5 & & \mathbf{1370184256} := (1 + 37018 - 4 + 2 + 5 - 6)^2 \\
 & := (-1 + 3 - 5 + 012 + 51 + 07)^5 & & := (-1 + 37018 - 4 + 2 - 5 + 6)^2 \\
 & := (-13 + 50 - 1 + 25 - 1 + 07)^5 & & \mathbf{1370258289} := (-1 + 37025 + 8 + 2 - 8 - 9)^2 \\
 & := (1 - 35 + 01 - 2 - 5 + 107)^5 & & := (-1 + 37025 - 8 + 2 + 8 - 9)^2 \\
 & := (-1 - 35 - 01 + 2 - 5 + 107)^5 & & := (1 + 37025 - 8 - 2 - 8 + 9)^2 \\
 & := (1 - 3 - 50 + 125 + 1 - 07)^5 & & := (-1 + 37025 + 82 - 89)^2 \\
 & := (-1 - 3 + 50 - 1 + 25 - 10 + 7)^5 & & \mathbf{1370554441} := (-1 + 37055 + 4 + 4 - 41)^2 \\
 & := (1 + 3 - 50 - 1 + 2 + 5 + 107)^5 & & \mathbf{1370776576} := (-1 + 37077 - 65 + 7 + 6)^2 \\
 & := (-1 + 3 - 50 + 1 + 2 + 5 + 107)^5 & & \mathbf{1370924676} := (-1 + 37092 - 4 - 67 + 6)^2 \\
 & := (13 + 50 + 12 - 5 - 10 + 7)^5 & & \mathbf{1370998729} := (1 + 37099 + 8 - 72 - 9)^2 \\
 \mathbf{1351371121} & := (1 - 351 + 37112 - 1)^2 & & := (-1 + 37099 - 8 - 72 + 9)^2 \\
 & := (-1 - 351 + 37112 + 1)^2 & & \mathbf{1371072784} := (1 + 37107 + 2 - 78 - 4)^2 \\
 \mathbf{1358291025} & := (1 + 35829 + 1025)^2 & & \mathbf{1371294961} := (1 + 37129 - 4 - 96 + 1)^2 \\
 \mathbf{1358954496} & := (-1 - 3 + 5 + 8 + 95 - 4 - 4 + 96)^4 & & \mathbf{1375036928} := (137 + 50 + 3 - 6 + 928)^3 \\
 & := (1 + 3 + 5 - 8 + 95 + 4 - 4 + 96)^4 & & := (-13 + 750 + 369 - 2 + 8)^3 \\
 & := (1 - 3 - 5 + 8 + 95 + 4 - 4 + 96)^4 & & \mathbf{1382469544} := (138 + 24 - 6 + 954 + 4)^3 \\
 & := (1 + 3 + 5 - 8 + 95 - 4 + 4 + 96)^4 & & \mathbf{1386195875} := (138 + 6 + 1 + 958 + 7 + 5)^3 \\
 & := (1 - 3 - 5 + 8 + 95 - 4 + 4 + 96)^4 & & := (138 + 6 + 1 + 95 + 875)^3 \\
 & := (-1 - 3 + 5 - 8 + 95 + 4 + 4 + 96)^4 & & := (13 + 8 + 61 + 958 + 75)^3 \\
 & := (135 - 8 + 9 + 5 - 4 + 49 + 6)^4 & & := (1 + 38 + 6 + 195 + 875)^3 \\
 & := (1 - 3 + 58 + 95 + 44 - 9 + 6)^4 & & \mathbf{1387488001} := (13 + 87 + 4 + 88 + 001)^4
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 & := (13 + 87 + 4 + 8 + 80 + 01)^4 & := (-1 + 4 + 53 + 9 - 3 - 3 - 5 + 6 + 8)^5 \\
 \mathbf{1389928896} & := (1 + 3 + 8 + 992 + 8 + 8 + 96)^3 & := (1 - 4 + 53 + 9 + 3 - 3 - 5 + 6 + 8)^5 \\
 & := (13 + 8 + 992 + 88 + 9 + 6)^3 & := (1 - 4 + 53 + 9 - 3 + 3 - 5 + 6 + 8)^5 \\
 & := (13 + 8 + 992 + 8 + 89 + 6)^3 & := (1 + 4 + 53 - 9 + 3 - 3 + 5 + 6 + 8)^5 \\
 & := (1 + 38 + 992 + 88 - 9 + 6)^3 & := (1 + 4 + 53 - 9 - 3 + 3 + 5 + 6 + 8)^5 \\
 & := (-1 + 38 + 992 - 8 + 89 + 6)^3 & := (1 + 4 + 5 + 39 + 3 - 3 + 5 + 6 + 8)^5 \\
 & := (1 + 3 + 89 + 928 + 89 + 6)^3 & := (1 + 4 + 5 + 39 - 3 + 3 + 5 + 6 + 8)^5 \\
 & := (138 - 9 + 92 + 889 + 6)^3 & := (1 + 4 - 5 - 3 + 93 - 3 - 5 - 6 - 8)^5 \\
 \mathbf{1397937321} & := (1 - 3 - 9 + 79 + 37321)^2 & := (-1 - 4 + 5 - 3 + 93 - 3 - 5 - 6 - 8)^5 \\
 \mathbf{1407375225} & := (1 + 4 - 07 + 37522 - 5)^2 & := (-1 - 4 - 5 - 3 + 93 - 3 + 5 - 6 - 8)^5 \\
 & := (-1 - 4 - 07 + 37522 + 5)^2 & := (1 + 4 + 5 - 3 + 9 + 33 + 5 + 6 + 8)^5 \\
 \mathbf{1416247867} & := (14 + 1 - 6 + 247 + 867)^3 & := (1 + 4 + 5 + 3 + 9 - 3 + 35 + 6 + 8)^5 \\
 \mathbf{1416468496} & := (1 + 4 + 164 + 6 + 8 - 4 + 9 + 6)^4 & := (1 + 4 + 5 - 3 + 9 + 3 + 35 + 6 + 8)^5 \\
 & := (1 - 4 + 164 + 6 + 8 + 4 + 9 + 6)^4 & := (-1 + 4 + 5 + 3 + 9 + 3 - 3 + 56 - 8)^5 \\
 & := (1 + 4 + 1 + 6 - 4 + 6 + 84 + 96)^4 & := (-1 + 4 + 5 + 3 + 9 - 3 + 3 + 56 - 8)^5 \\
 & := (1 - 4 + 1 + 6 + 4 + 6 + 84 + 96)^4 & := (-1 + 4 + 5 - 3 + 9 + 3 + 3 + 56 - 8)^5 \\
 & := (141 + 6 + 46 + 8 - 4 - 9 + 6)^4 & := (1 - 4 + 5 + 3 + 9 + 3 + 3 + 56 - 8)^5 \\
 & := (141 - 6 - 4 - 6 + 84 - 9 - 6)^4 & := (-1 + 4 - 5 + 3 + 9 - 3 - 3 + 56 + 8)^5 \\
 & := (-1 + 41 + 64 + 6 - 8 - 4 + 96)^4 & := (1 + 4 + 5 + 3 - 9 + 3 - 3 + 56 + 8)^5 \\
 & := (1 + 41 + 6 + 46 + 8 - 4 + 96)^4 & := (-1 + 4 - 5 - 3 + 9 + 3 - 3 + 56 + 8)^5 \\
 & := (14 + 16 + 4 + 68 - 4 + 96)^4 & := (1 - 4 - 5 + 3 + 9 + 3 - 3 + 56 + 8)^5 \\
 & := (14 + 16 - 4 + 68 + 4 + 96)^4 & := (1 + 4 + 5 + 3 - 9 - 3 + 3 + 56 + 8)^5 \\
 & := (1 + 4 + 164 + 68 - 49 + 6)^4 & := (-1 + 4 - 5 - 3 + 9 - 3 + 3 + 56 + 8)^5 \\
 & := (-14 - 1 - 646 + 849 + 6)^4 & := (1 - 4 - 5 + 3 + 9 - 3 + 3 + 56 + 8)^5 \\
 \mathbf{1423828125} & := (1423 + 8 - 281 - 25)^3 & := (1 + 4 + 5 - 3 - 9 + 3 + 3 + 56 + 8)^5 \\
 & := (-1 + 423 + 828 - 125)^3 & := (1 - 4 - 5 - 3 + 9 + 3 + 3 + 56 + 8)^5 \\
 \mathbf{1427628376} & := (1 + 4 + 276 + 2 + 837 + 6)^3 & := (-1 + 45 + 39 - 3 - 3 + 5 - 6 - 8)^5 \\
 \mathbf{1437850561} & := (-1 + 4 + 37850 + 5 + 61)^2 & := (1 - 45 + 3 + 93 - 3 + 5 + 6 + 8)^5 \\
 & := (14 + 37850 + 56 - 1)^2 & := (1 - 45 - 3 + 93 + 3 + 5 + 6 + 8)^5 \\
 \mathbf{1441037521} & := (-1 + 441 + 037521)^2 & := (-1 + 45 - 3 - 9 + 33 + 5 + 6 - 8)^5 \\
 \mathbf{1445900625} & := (-1 + 44 + 5 + 90 + 062 - 5)^4 & := (-1 + 45 + 3 - 9 + 33 - 5 - 6 + 8)^5 \\
 & := (-1 + 44 - 5 + 90 + 062 + 5)^4 & := (-1 + 45 - 3 + 9 - 3 + 35 - 6 - 8)^5 \\
 & := (-1 + 4 + 45 + 90 + 062 - 5)^4 & := (-1 + 45 + 3 - 9 - 3 + 35 + 6 - 8)^5 \\
 \mathbf{1453933568} & := (-1 + 4 + 53 + 9 + 3 - 3 + 5 + 6 - 8)^5 & := (-1 + 45 - 3 - 9 + 3 + 35 + 6 - 8)^5 \\
 & := (-1 + 4 + 53 + 9 - 3 + 3 + 5 + 6 - 8)^5 & := (1 + 45 - 3 - 9 - 3 + 35 - 6 + 8)^5 \\
 & := (1 - 4 + 53 + 9 + 3 + 3 + 5 + 6 - 8)^5 & := (-14 - 5 + 39 + 3 - 3 + 56 - 8)^5 \\
 & := (-1 + 4 + 53 + 9 + 3 + 3 - 5 - 6 + 8)^5 & := (-14 - 5 + 39 - 3 + 3 + 56 - 8)^5 \\
 & := (1 + 4 + 53 + 9 - 3 - 3 + 5 - 6 + 8)^5 & := (14 - 5 + 3 + 93 - 35 + 6 - 8)^5
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 & := (-14 - 5 - 3 + 9 + 33 + 56 - 8)^5 & := (-1 - 4 - 7 + 5 - 7 + 8 + 9 + 05 + 6)^8 \\
 & := (-1 + 45 - 39 + 3 - 3 - 5 + 68)^5 & := (-1 + 4 - 75 + 78 + 9 + 05 - 6)^8 \\
 & := (-1 + 45 - 39 - 3 + 3 - 5 + 68)^5 & := (1 - 4 + 75 - 78 + 9 + 05 + 6)^8 \\
 & := (1 - 45 + 39 + 3 - 3 + 5 + 68)^5 & := (-1 - 4 - 75 + 7 + 8 + 90 - 5 - 6)^8 \\
 & := (1 - 45 + 39 - 3 + 3 + 5 + 68)^5 & := (1 - 4 - 75 - 7 + 8 + 90 - 5 + 6)^8 \\
 & := (-1 + 45 - 3 + 93 - 3 + 5 - 68)^5 & := (-1 + 4 + 75 + 7 + 8 - 90 + 5 + 6)^8 \\
 & := (-1 + 45 + 3 - 9 - 33 - 5 + 68)^5 & := (-1 + 4 - 75 - 7 - 8 + 90 + 5 + 6)^8 \\
 & := (1 - 45 - 3 + 9 + 33 + 5 + 68)^5 & := (1 + 4 + 75 + 7 + 8 + 90 + 5 + 6)^4 \\
 & := (-1 + 45 + 3 - 9 - 3 - 35 + 68)^5 & := (1 + 4 + 75 + 7 - 8 - 9 - 056)^8 \\
 & := (-1 + 45 - 3 - 9 + 3 - 35 + 68)^5 & := (-1 + 4 + 75 - 7 + 8 - 9 - 056)^8 \\
 & := (1 - 45 + 3 + 9 - 3 + 35 + 68)^5 & := (1 - 4 - 7 - 57 - 8 + 90 + 5 - 6)^8 \\
 & := (1 - 45 - 3 + 9 + 3 + 35 + 68)^5 & := (-1 - 4 - 7 - 57 - 8 + 90 - 5 + 6)^8 \\
 & := (-1 - 4 - 53 + 93 + 35 + 6 - 8)^5 & := (1 + 4 + 7 + 57 - 8 + 9 - 056)^8 \\
 & := (-1 + 4 - 5 + 39 - 33 + 56 + 8)^5 & := (-1 + 4 - 7 + 57 + 8 + 9 - 056)^8 \\
 & := (1 + 4 + 5 - 39 + 33 + 56 + 8)^5 & := (1 + 4 - 7 - 57 + 8 + 9 + 056)^8 \\
 & := (-1 + 45 + 39 + 33 - 56 + 8)^5 & := (1 + 4 - 7 + 5 - 78 + 90 + 5 - 6)^8 \\
 & := (-1 - 4 - 53 + 93 - 35 + 68)^5 & := (-1 + 4 - 7 + 5 - 78 + 90 - 5 + 6)^8 \\
 & := (1 + 4 + 53 - 93 + 35 + 68)^5 & := (-1 + 4 + 7 + 5 + 78 - 90 + 5 + 6)^8 \\
 & := (-1 + 45 + 441 + 9 + 637)^3 & := (-1 + 4 - 7 - 5 - 78 + 90 + 5 + 6)^8 \\
 & := (-14 - 5 - 63 + 38244)^2 & := (1 + 4 + 7 + 5 + 78 + 90 + 5 + 6)^4 \\
 & := (-145 + 63 + 38244)^2 & := (-1 + 4 - 7 + 5 + 78 - 9 - 056)^8 \\
 & := (-147 - 3 - 6 + 38544)^2 & := (-1 - 4 - 7 - 5 + 78 + 9 - 056)^8 \\
 & := (1 + 4 + 7 + 5 + 7 - 8 + 9 - 05 - 6)^8 & := (1 - 4 - 7 + 5 - 7 - 8 + 90 - 56)^8 \\
 & := (-1 + 4 + 7 + 5 - 7 + 8 + 9 - 05 - 6)^8 & := (14 + 75 + 7 + 89 + 05 + 6)^4 \\
 & := (-1 + 4 - 7 + 5 + 7 + 8 + 9 - 05 - 6)^8 & := (-14 + 7 - 57 + 89 - 05 - 6)^8 \\
 & := (1 - 4 + 7 + 5 + 7 + 8 - 9 + 05 - 6)^8 & := (-14 + 7 - 5 - 7 + 89 - 056)^8 \\
 & := (1 + 4 + 7 - 5 + 7 - 8 + 9 + 05 - 6)^8 & := (-14 - 7 - 5 + 7 + 89 - 056)^8 \\
 & := (-1 - 4 + 7 + 5 + 7 - 8 + 9 + 05 - 6)^8 & := (-1 + 47 + 57 - 8 + 90 + 5 + 6)^4 \\
 & := (-1 + 4 + 7 - 5 - 7 + 8 + 9 + 05 - 6)^8 & := (1 + 47 + 5 + 78 + 9 + 056)^4 \\
 & := (-1 + 4 - 7 - 5 + 7 + 8 + 9 + 05 - 6)^8 & := (-1 + 47 + 5 + 7 - 8 + 90 + 56)^4 \\
 & := (1 + 4 + 7 - 5 + 7 + 8 - 9 - 05 + 6)^8 & := (1 - 4 - 7 + 57 - 89 + 056)^8 \\
 & := (-1 - 4 + 7 + 5 + 7 + 8 - 9 - 05 + 6)^8 & := (147 + 5 + 7 - 89 - 056)^8 \\
 & := (-1 + 4 + 7 - 5 + 7 - 8 + 9 - 05 + 6)^8 & := (147 + 5 + 78 - 90 + 56)^4 \\
 & := (1 + 4 - 7 + 5 - 7 + 8 + 9 - 05 + 6)^8 & := (1 + 477 + 648 - 6 + 19)^3 \\
 & := (-1 - 4 + 7 - 5 + 7 + 8 - 9 + 05 + 6)^8 & := (1 + 477 - 6 + 48 + 619)^3 \\
 & := (1 - 4 + 7 + 5 - 7 - 8 + 9 + 05 + 6)^8 & := (-148 + 38674 - 4 - 1)^2 \\
 & := (1 - 4 - 7 + 5 + 7 - 8 + 9 + 05 + 6)^8 & := (1 + 4 + 971 + 93 - 9 + 84)^3 \\
 & := (1 + 4 - 7 - 5 - 7 + 8 + 9 + 05 + 6)^8 & := (1 + 4 - 9 + 71 + 93 + 984)^3
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 & := (-14 + 971 + 93 + 98 - 4)^3 & & := (-1 + 54 + 4 - 8 - 04 - 4 - 1 - 6)^6 \\
 & := (14 + 9 + 719 + 398 + 4)^3 & & := (-1 + 54 - 4 - 8 + 04 - 4 - 1 - 6)^6 \\
 & := (1 + 49 + 71 + 939 + 84)^3 & & := (-1 + 54 - 4 - 8 - 04 + 4 - 1 - 6)^6 \\
 \mathbf{1498386681} & := (1 + 49 - 8 + 38668 - 1)^2 & & := (-1 - 5 + 4 + 4 + 8 + 04 + 4 + 16)^6 \\
 & := (-1 + 49 - 8 + 38668 + 1)^2 & & := (-15 + 44 + 8 - 04 - 4 - 1 + 6)^6 \\
 \mathbf{1501123625} & := (1501 - 1 + 2 - 362 + 5)^3 & & := (-15 + 44 - 8 + 04 + 4 - 1 + 6)^6 \\
 \mathbf{1506138481} & := (150 + 61 - 3 - 8 + 4 - 8 + 1)^4 & & := (-15 + 4 + 48 - 04 - 4 - 1 + 6)^6 \\
 & := (150 + 6 - 1 + 3 - 8 + 48 - 1)^4 & & := (-15 - 4 + 48 + 04 - 4 - 1 + 6)^6 \\
 & := (150 - 6 + 1 - 3 + 8 + 48 - 1)^4 & & := (-15 - 4 + 48 - 04 + 4 - 1 + 6)^6 \\
 & := (150 - 6 - 1 - 3 + 8 + 48 + 1)^4 & & := (-15 + 4 + 4 - 8 + 044 - 1 + 6)^6 \\
 & := (1 + 5 + 06 + 138 + 48 - 1)^4 & & := (-15 - 4 - 4 + 8 + 044 - 1 + 6)^6 \\
 & := (-1 + 5 + 06 + 138 + 48 + 1)^4 & & := (1 - 54 + 4 + 80 + 4 + 4 + 1 - 6)^6 \\
 & := (1 + 50 + 61 + 38 + 48 - 1)^4 & & := (-1 - 54 + 4 + 80 + 4 - 4 - 1 + 6)^6 \\
 & := (-1 + 50 + 61 + 38 + 48 + 1)^4 & & := (-1 - 54 + 4 + 80 - 4 + 4 - 1 + 6)^6 \\
 & := (1 + 50 - 6 - 13 + 84 + 81)^4 & & := (-1 - 54 - 4 + 80 + 4 + 4 - 1 + 6)^6 \\
 & := (150 - 6 + 138 - 4 - 81)^4 & & := (-1 + 54 + 4 + 8 + 04 - 41 + 6)^6 \\
 \mathbf{1516910949} & := (1 - 5 - 1 + 69 + 1094 - 9)^3 & & := (1 + 5 + 44 + 8 - 04 - 4 - 16)^6 \\
 & := (-1 - 5 + 1 + 69 + 1094 - 9)^3 & & := (1 + 5 + 44 - 8 + 04 + 4 - 16)^6 \\
 \mathbf{1518037444} & := (1518 + 037444)^2 & & := (1 + 5 + 4 + 48 - 04 - 4 - 16)^6 \\
 \mathbf{1532808577} & := (1 + 5 + 3 + 280 + 857 + 7)^3 & & := (1 + 5 - 4 + 48 + 04 - 4 - 16)^6 \\
 \mathbf{1536953616} & := (153 - 6 + 9 + 53 - 6 + 1 - 6)^4 & & := (1 + 5 - 4 + 48 - 04 + 4 - 16)^6 \\
 & := (153 + 6 - 9 + 5 + 36 + 1 + 6)^4 & & := (1 + 5 + 4 + 4 - 8 + 044 - 16)^6 \\
 & := (153 + 6 + 9 + 5 + 3 + 6 + 16)^4 & & := (1 + 5 - 4 - 4 + 8 + 044 - 16)^6 \\
 & := (1 + 53 + 69 + 5 + 3 + 61 + 6)^4 & & := (-15 - 44 + 80 + 4 + 4 - 1 + 6)^6 \\
 & := (1 + 53 + 6 + 95 + 36 + 1 + 6)^4 & & := (-15 + 4 + 4 + 80 - 44 - 1 + 6)^6 \\
 & := (1 + 5 + 3 + 69 + 53 + 61 + 6)^4 & & := (-15 + 4 + 4 + 80 - 4 - 41 + 6)^6 \\
 & := (153 + 69 + 5 - 36 + 1 + 6)^4 & & := (-15 + 4 - 4 + 80 + 4 - 41 + 6)^6 \\
 & := (153 + 69 - 5 + 3 - 6 - 16)^4 & & := (-15 - 4 + 4 + 80 + 4 - 41 + 6)^6 \\
 & := (15 + 36 + 95 - 3 + 61 - 6)^4 & & := (1 - 54 + 48 + 044 + 1 - 6)^6 \\
 & := (1 + 53 + 69 + 53 + 6 + 16)^4 & & := (1 - 54 + 48 + 04 + 41 - 6)^6 \\
 & := (15 + 36 + 95 + 36 + 16)^4 & & := (1 + 5 - 44 + 80 + 4 + 4 - 16)^6 \\
 & := (-1 + 5 - 369 - 53 + 616)^4 & & := (1 + 5 + 4 + 4 + 80 - 44 - 16)^6 \\
 & := (15 - 369 + 536 + 16)^4 & & := (1 + 5 + 448 - 04 - 416)^6 \\
 & := (-1 + 536 - 953 + 616)^4 & & := (-15 + 4 + 480 - 441 + 6)^6 \\
 \mathbf{1539228289} & := (-1 + 5 + 39228 + 2 + 8 - 9)^2 & & := (1544 - 804 + 416)^3 \\
 & := (1 + 5 + 39228 - 2 - 8 + 9)^2 & & \\
 \mathbf{1543939849} & := (-154 + 39398 + 49)^2 & & \mathbf{1549839424} := (-1 - 54 - 9 + 8 + 39424)^2 \\
 & & & := (-15 - 49 + 8 + 39424)^2 \\
 \mathbf{1544804416} & := (15 + 4 + 4 + 8 + 04 + 4 + 1 - 6)^6 & & := (-154 + 98 + 39424)^2
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 \mathbf{1552836312} &:= (-1 + 5 + 528 - 3 + 631 - 2)^3 & &:= (1 - 5 - 6 + 40 + 3 - 13 + 49)^5 \\
 &:= (-1 - 5 + 528 + 3 + 631 + 2)^3 & &:= (156 - 40 - 31 - 3 - 4 - 9)^5 \\
 \mathbf{1553936400} &:= (1 + 55 + 39364 + 00)^2 & &:= (156 - 40 - 3 - 1 - 34 - 9)^5 \\
 \mathbf{1556862679} &:= (1 + 556 - 8 + 626 - 7 - 9)^3 & &:= (156 - 4 - 031 - 3 - 49)^5 \\
 \mathbf{1560896000} &:= (1 + 560 + 8 - 9 + 600 + 0)^3 & \mathbf{1566338929} &:= (-15 + 663 + 38929)^2 \\
 &:= (-1 + 560 - 8 + 9 + 600 + 0)^3 & \mathbf{1568239201} &:= (1 + 5 - 6 + 8 + 2 - 3 - 9 + 201)^4 \\
 \mathbf{1564031349} &:= (-1 + 56 + 4 + 03 - 1 + 3 - 4 + 9)^5 & &:= (-1 - 5 + 6 + 8 + 2 - 3 - 9 + 201)^4 \\
 &:= (1 + 56 + 4 - 03 + 1 - 3 + 4 + 9)^5 & &:= (-1 + 5 - 6 + 8 - 2 + 3 - 9 + 201)^4 \\
 &:= (-1 + 56 - 4 + 03 - 1 + 3 + 4 + 9)^5 & &:= (-1 + 5 + 6 - 8 + 2 + 3 - 9 + 201)^4 \\
 &:= (15 + 64 - 03 + 1 - 3 + 4 - 9)^5 & &:= (1 - 5 + 6 - 8 - 2 - 3 + 9 + 201)^4 \\
 &:= (-15 + 64 + 03 + 1 + 3 + 4 + 9)^5 & &:= (-1 + 5 - 6 - 8 + 2 - 3 + 9 + 201)^4 \\
 &:= (15 + 6 + 40 - 3 + 1 - 3 + 4 + 9)^5 & &:= (156 + 8 + 23 + 9 + 2 + 01)^4 \\
 &:= (15 - 6 + 40 + 3 + 1 + 3 + 4 + 9)^5 & &:= (156 + 8 + 2 + 3 + 9 + 20 + 1)^4 \\
 &:= (15 + 6 + 4 - 03 + 1 - 3 + 49)^5 & &:= (15 + 6 + 82 + 3 + 92 + 01)^4 \\
 &:= (15 - 6 + 4 + 03 + 1 + 3 + 49)^5 & &:= (156 - 8 + 23 + 9 + 20 - 1)^4 \\
 &:= (-1 - 5 + 64 + 03 + 13 + 4 - 9)^5 & &:= (156 + 8 + 23 - 9 + 20 + 1)^4 \\
 &:= (1 + 5 - 6 + 40 + 31 + 3 + 4 - 9)^5 & &:= (15 + 68 + 23 + 92 + 01)^4 \\
 &:= (-1 - 5 + 6 + 40 + 31 + 3 + 4 - 9)^5 & &:= (1 + 56 + 82 + 39 + 20 + 1)^4 \\
 &:= (1 - 5 - 6 + 40 + 31 + 3 - 4 + 9)^5 & \mathbf{1568397609} &:= (-156 + 8 + 39760 - 9)^2 \\
 &:= (-1 - 5 - 6 + 40 + 31 - 3 + 4 + 9)^5 & \mathbf{1568983528} &:= (156 + 8 + 983 + 5 + 2 + 8)^3 \\
 &:= (1 + 5 - 6 + 40 + 3 + 13 + 4 + 9)^5 & \mathbf{1572439716} &:= (1 - 57 - 2 - 4 + 39716)^2 \\
 &:= (-1 - 5 + 6 + 40 + 3 + 13 + 4 + 9)^5 & &:= (1 + 5 - 72 + 4 + 39716)^2 \\
 &:= (1 - 5 + 6 + 40 + 3 - 1 + 34 - 9)^5 & \mathbf{1581167125} &:= (1 - 5 + 8 + 1167 + 1 - 2 - 5)^3 \\
 &:= (1 + 5 - 6 + 40 + 3 + 1 + 34 - 9)^5 & &:= (-1 - 5 + 8 + 1167 - 1 + 2 - 5)^3 \\
 &:= (-1 - 5 + 6 + 40 + 3 + 1 + 34 - 9)^5 & &:= (-1 + 5 - 8 + 1167 - 1 - 2 + 5)^3 \\
 &:= (1 - 5 - 6 + 40 - 3 - 1 + 34 + 9)^5 & \mathbf{1588739881} &:= (-15 + 8 - 8 - 7 + 39881)^2 \\
 &:= (-1 - 5 - 6 + 40 - 3 + 1 + 34 + 9)^5 & &:= (-15 - 8 + 8 - 7 + 39881)^2 \\
 &:= (-1 - 5 - 6 + 4 + 031 - 3 + 49)^5 & \mathbf{1593413632} &:= (-159 - 34 + 1363 - 2)^3 \\
 &:= (1 - 5 - 6 - 4 + 031 + 3 + 49)^5 & \mathbf{1599840004} &:= (-1 + 5 - 9 - 9 + 8 + 40004)^2 \\
 &:= (1 + 5 - 6 + 4 + 03 + 13 + 49)^5 & \mathbf{1622234375} &:= (1622 - 2 - 3 - 437 - 5)^3 \\
 &:= (-1 - 5 + 6 + 4 + 03 + 13 + 49)^5 & \mathbf{1626379776} &:= (162 + 6 + 37 + 977 - 6)^3 \\
 &:= (-15 - 6 + 40 + 3 + 1 - 3 + 49)^5 & &:= (162 - 6 + 37 + 977 + 6)^3 \\
 &:= (-15 - 6 + 40 - 3 + 1 + 3 + 49)^5 & &:= (1 - 6 + 26 + 379 + 776)^3 \\
 &:= (15 - 6 + 4 + 031 + 34 - 9)^5 & &:= (1626 - 379 - 77 + 6)^3 \\
 &:= (-15 + 6 + 4 + 031 + 34 + 9)^5 & \mathbf{1632240801} &:= (-16 - 32 + 240 + 8 + 01)^4 \\
 &:= (-1 + 56 - 40 + 3 - 1 + 3 + 49)^5 & \mathbf{1634691752} &:= (163 + 46 + 917 + 52)^3 \\
 &:= (-1 - 56 + 4 - 03 + 134 - 9)^5 & \mathbf{1638858339} &:= (-1 - 6 - 3 - 8 + 858 + 339)^3 \\
 &:= (1 - 56 - 4 + 03 + 134 - 9)^5 & \mathbf{1647212741} &:= (-16 - 4 - 72 + 1274 - 1)^3
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 & := (-164 + 72 + 1274 - 1)^3 & & := (1 + 73 + 189 + 1 - 4 - 56)^4 \\
 \mathbf{1649740689} & := (-16 - 49 - 7 + 40689)^2 & & := (1 + 73 - 18 + 9 + 145 - 6)^4 \\
 & := (1 - 6 - 51 + 040689)^2 & & := (1 + 73 - 1 + 89 - 14 + 56)^4 \\
 & := (-1 - 65 + 10 + 40689)^2 & & := (-1 + 73 + 1 + 89 - 14 + 56)^4 \\
 \mathbf{1655595487} & := (1 + 655 - 5 - 9 + 548 - 7)^3 & & \mathbf{1745337664} := (-1 - 7 + 453 - 3 + 766 - 4)^3 \\
 \mathbf{1664006625} & := (166 + 400 - 6 + 625)^3 & & \mathbf{1748410596} := (1 + 748 + 41059 + 6)^2 \\
 \mathbf{1664966416} & := (166 + 4 + 9 + 6 + 6 + 4 + 1 + 6)^4 & & \mathbf{1754049816} := (175 + 40 + 4 + 981 + 6)^3 \\
 & := (166 + 49 - 6 - 6 + 4 + 1 - 6)^4 & & \mathbf{1764420025} := (-1 + 7 + 6 - 4 + 42002 - 5)^2 \\
 & := (166 + 4 + 9 - 6 - 6 + 41 - 6)^4 & & & := (1 + 7 - 6 - 4 + 42002 + 5)^2 \\
 & := (166 - 4 + 9 + 66 - 41 + 6)^4 & & \mathbf{1766100625} := (176 + 6 + 10 + 06 + 2 + 5)^4 \\
 & := (16 + 64 + 96 + 6 + 4 + 16)^4 & & & := (1 + 76 + 61 + 0062 + 5)^4 \\
 & := (16 + 64 + 9 + 66 + 41 + 6)^4 & & & := (1 + 7 + 66 + 100 + 6 + 25)^4 \\
 & := (16 + 6 + 4 + 96 + 64 + 16)^4 & & \mathbf{1771561000} := (1771 - 561 + 000)^3 \\
 & := (1 + 66 + 49 + 66 + 4 + 16)^4 & & \mathbf{1775956931} := (1775 + 9 - 569 - 3 - 1)^3 \\
 & := (1 + 66 + 49 + 6 + 64 + 16)^4 & & & := (1 - 77 + 595 + 693 - 1)^3 \\
 \mathbf{1680914269} & := (1 + 680 + 91 + 426 - 9)^3 & & & := (-1 - 77 + 595 + 693 + 1)^3 \\
 \mathbf{1681410025} & := (1 + 6 - 8 - 1 + 41002 + 5)^2 & & \mathbf{1786414756} := (-1 + 786 + 41475 + 6)^2 \\
 & := (-1 + 6 - 8 + 1 + 41002 + 5)^2 & & \mathbf{1800814096} := (180 + 08 - 1 + 4 + 09 + 6)^4 \\
 \mathbf{1689410871} & := (1689 - 410 - 87 - 1)^3 & & & := (-1 + 80 - 08 - 1 + 40 + 96)^4 \\
 \mathbf{1693240201} & := (16 + 932 + 40201)^2 & & & := (180 + 081 - 40 - 9 - 6)^4 \\
 \mathbf{1698181681} & := (-1 - 6 + 98 + 181 - 68 - 1)^4 & & \mathbf{1801088541} := (18 + 01 + 08 - 8 + 5 - 4 + 1)^7 \\
 & := (-16 + 981 - 81 - 681)^4 & & & := (18 + 01 - 08 + 8 + 5 - 4 + 1)^7 \\
 \mathbf{1710777536} & := (1 + 7 + 1077 + 75 + 36)^3 & & & := (-1 + 8 - 010 + 8 + 8 + 5 + 4 - 1)^7 \\
 \mathbf{1719374392} & := (1 + 719 + 37 + 439 + 2)^3 & & & := (1 + 8 + 010 + 8 - 8 + 5 - 4 + 1)^7 \\
 \mathbf{1731891456} & := (1 + 7 + 3 + 189 + 1 + 4 + 5 - 6)^4 & & & := (1 + 8 + 010 - 8 + 8 + 5 - 4 + 1)^7 \\
 & := (1 + 7 + 3 + 189 - 1 + 4 - 5 + 6)^4 & & & := (1 - 8 + 010 + 8 + 8 + 5 - 4 + 1)^7 \\
 & := (-1 + 7 + 3 + 189 + 1 + 4 - 5 + 6)^4 & & & := (-1 - 8 + 010 - 8 - 8 - 5 + 41)^7 \\
 & := (-1 + 7 + 3 + 189 - 1 - 4 + 5 + 6)^4 & & & := (1 - 80 + 108 - 8 + 5 - 4 - 1)^7 \\
 & := (173 + 18 + 9 + 1 + 4 + 5 - 6)^4 & & & := (-1 - 80 + 108 - 8 + 5 - 4 + 1)^7 \\
 & := (173 + 18 + 9 - 1 + 4 - 5 + 6)^4 & & & := (1 - 80 + 108 - 8 - 5 + 4 + 1)^7 \\
 & := (173 + 1 + 8 + 9 + 14 + 5 - 6)^4 & & & := (1 - 80 + 10 + 88 + 5 - 4 + 1)^7 \\
 & := (173 - 1 + 8 + 9 + 14 - 5 + 6)^4 & & & := (1 - 80 + 10 + 8 + 85 - 4 + 1)^7 \\
 & := (1 + 73 + 1 + 89 + 1 + 45 - 6)^4 & & & := (1 - 8 + 0108 - 85 + 4 + 1)^7 \\
 & := (-1 - 7 + 318 - 91 - 4 - 5 - 6)^4 & & \mathbf{1804229351} := (1 + 80 + 4 + 2 + 2 - 9 - 3 - 5 - 1)^5 \\
 & := (173 - 18 + 9 + 1 + 45 - 6)^4 & & & := (-1 + 80 - 4 - 2 - 2 + 9 - 3 - 5 - 1)^5 \\
 & := (173 + 1 + 89 + 1 - 4 - 56)^4 & & & := (-1 + 80 + 4 + 2 - 2 - 9 + 3 - 5 - 1)^5 \\
 & := (173 - 1 - 8 + 91 - 45 - 6)^4 & & & := (-1 + 80 + 4 - 2 + 2 - 9 + 3 - 5 - 1)^5 \\
 & := (17 + 31 + 8 + 9 + 145 - 6)^4 & & & := (-1 + 80 + 4 - 2 - 2 - 9 - 3 + 5 - 1)^5
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} &:= (-1 + 80 - 4 + 2 + 2 - 9 - 3 + 5 - 1)^5 \\ &:= (1 + 80 - 4 - 2 - 2 - 9 + 3 + 5 - 1)^5 \\ &:= (-1 + 80 + 4 + 2 + 2 - 9 - 3 - 5 + 1)^5 \\ &:= (1 + 80 + 4 - 2 - 2 - 9 + 3 - 5 + 1)^5 \\ &:= (1 + 80 - 4 + 2 + 2 - 9 + 3 - 5 + 1)^5 \\ &:= (1 + 80 - 4 + 2 - 2 - 9 - 3 + 5 + 1)^5 \\ &:= (1 + 80 - 4 - 2 + 2 - 9 - 3 + 5 + 1)^5 \\ &:= (-1 + 80 - 4 - 2 - 2 - 9 + 3 + 5 + 1)^5 \\ &:= (1 + 8 + 042 + 2 + 9 + 3 + 5 + 1)^5 \\ &:= (-18 - 04 - 2 - 2 + 93 + 5 - 1)^5 \\ &:= (-18 + 04 - 2 - 2 + 93 - 5 + 1)^5 \\ &:= (-18 - 04 + 2 + 2 + 93 - 5 + 1)^5 \\ &:= (18 + 04 + 2 + 2 + 9 + 35 + 1)^5 \\ &:= (18 - 04 + 2 - 2 + 9 - 3 + 51)^5 \\ &:= (18 - 04 - 2 + 2 + 9 - 3 + 51)^5 \\ &:= (18 + 04 + 2 + 2 - 9 + 3 + 51)^5 \\ &:= (-1 + 80 + 4 - 22 + 9 - 3 + 5 - 1)^5 \\ &:= (1 + 80 - 4 - 22 + 9 + 3 + 5 - 1)^5 \\ &:= (1 + 80 + 4 - 22 + 9 + 3 - 5 + 1)^5 \\ &:= (-1 + 80 - 4 - 22 + 9 + 3 + 5 + 1)^5 \\ &:= (1 + 8 + 042 + 29 - 3 - 5 - 1)^5 \\ &:= (1 - 8 + 042 + 29 + 3 + 5 - 1)^5 \\ &:= (-1 + 8 + 042 + 29 - 3 - 5 + 1)^5 \\ &:= (-1 - 8 + 042 + 29 + 3 + 5 + 1)^5 \\ &:= (18 - 042 - 2 + 93 + 5 - 1)^5 \\ &:= (-18 + 042 + 2 + 9 + 35 + 1)^5 \\ &:= (-18 + 042 + 2 - 9 + 3 + 51)^5 \\ &:= (18 + 04 + 22 - 9 + 35 + 1)^5 \\ &:= (-18 + 04 + 22 + 9 + 3 + 51)^5 \\ &:= (-18 + 04 + 2 + 29 + 3 + 51)^5 \\ &:= (1 + 80 - 42 + 29 - 3 + 5 + 1)^5 \\ &:= (-1 - 80 + 4 + 2 + 2 + 93 + 51)^5 \\ &:= (1 + 8 + 0422 - 9 - 351)^5 \\ &:= (-1 - 8 + 0422 + 9 - 351)^5 \end{aligned}$$

$$\mathbf{1818425449} := (1 + 81 + 8 + 42544 + 9)^2$$

$$\mathbf{1824793048} := (-1824 + 7 - 9 + 3048)^3$$

$$\mathbf{1836036801} := (183 + 6 + 03 + 6 + 8 + 01)^4$$

$$:= (1 + 83 + 6 + 036 + 80 + 1)^4$$

$$\begin{aligned} &:= (183 - 60 - 3 + 6 + 80 + 1)^4 \\ &:= (18 - 3 - 603 - 6 + 801)^4 \\ \mathbf{1838265625} &:= (18 - 3 + 8 + 2 + 6 + 5 + 6 - 2 - 5)^6 \\ &:= (18 + 3 + 8 + 2 + 6 - 5 + 6 + 2 - 5)^6 \\ &:= (18 - 3 + 8 - 2 + 6 + 5 + 6 + 2 - 5)^6 \\ &:= (18 + 3 + 8 - 2 + 6 + 5 - 6 - 2 + 5)^6 \\ &:= (18 - 3 + 8 + 2 + 6 - 5 + 6 - 2 + 5)^6 \\ &:= (18 + 3 + 8 - 2 - 6 + 5 + 6 - 2 + 5)^6 \\ &:= (18 + 3 - 8 + 2 + 6 + 5 + 6 - 2 + 5)^6 \\ &:= (18 - 3 + 8 - 2 + 6 - 5 + 6 + 2 + 5)^6 \\ &:= (18 + 3 - 8 - 2 + 6 + 5 + 6 + 2 + 5)^6 \\ &:= (-1 + 8 + 38 + 2 + 6 - 5 - 6 - 2 - 5)^6 \\ &:= (1 + 8 + 38 + 2 - 6 + 5 - 6 - 2 - 5)^6 \\ &:= (-1 + 8 + 38 + 2 - 6 - 5 + 6 - 2 - 5)^6 \\ &:= (-1 + 8 + 38 - 2 + 6 - 5 - 6 + 2 - 5)^6 \\ &:= (1 + 8 + 38 - 2 - 6 + 5 - 6 + 2 - 5)^6 \\ &:= (1 - 8 + 38 + 2 + 6 + 5 - 6 + 2 - 5)^6 \\ &:= (-1 + 8 + 38 - 2 - 6 - 5 + 6 + 2 - 5)^6 \\ &:= (-1 - 8 + 38 + 2 + 6 - 5 + 6 + 2 - 5)^6 \\ &:= (1 - 8 + 38 + 2 - 6 + 5 + 6 + 2 - 5)^6 \\ &:= (1 + 8 + 38 + 2 - 6 - 5 - 6 - 2 + 5)^6 \\ &:= (-1 - 8 + 38 - 2 + 6 + 5 - 6 - 2 + 5)^6 \\ &:= (-1 - 8 + 38 - 2 - 6 + 5 + 6 - 2 + 5)^6 \\ &:= (1 + 8 + 38 - 2 - 6 - 5 - 6 + 2 + 5)^6 \\ &:= (1 - 8 + 38 + 2 + 6 - 5 - 6 + 2 + 5)^6 \\ &:= (1 - 8 + 38 + 2 - 6 - 5 + 6 + 2 + 5)^6 \\ &:= (1 - 8 - 3 - 8 - 2 + 6 + 56 - 2 - 5)^6 \\ &:= (-1 - 8 + 3 - 8 + 2 - 6 + 56 + 2 - 5)^6 \\ &:= (-1 - 8 - 3 - 8 + 2 - 6 + 56 - 2 + 5)^6 \\ &:= (-1 - 8 - 3 - 8 - 2 - 6 + 56 + 2 + 5)^6 \\ &:= (18 - 3 + 8 + 26 - 5 - 6 + 2 - 5)^6 \\ &:= (18 + 3 - 8 + 26 + 5 - 6 + 2 - 5)^6 \\ &:= (18 - 3 - 8 + 26 + 5 - 6 - 2 + 5)^6 \\ &:= (18 + 3 - 8 + 26 - 5 - 6 + 2 + 5)^6 \\ &:= (-18 + 3 - 8 + 2 + 65 - 6 + 2 - 5)^6 \\ &:= (-18 - 3 - 8 + 2 + 65 - 6 - 2 + 5)^6 \\ &:= (-18 - 3 - 8 - 2 + 65 - 6 + 2 + 5)^6 \\ &:= (-18 - 3 + 8 + 2 - 6 - 5 + 62 - 5)^6 \end{aligned}$$

$:= (-18 + 3 - 8 + 2 - 6 + 5 + 62 - 5)^6$	$:= (18 - 38 - 2 - 6 + 56 + 2 + 5)^6$
$:= (-18 + 3 - 8 + 2 - 6 - 5 + 62 + 5)^6$	$:= (18 - 3 + 82 - 65 + 6 + 2 - 5)^6$
$:= (-18 - 3 - 8 - 2 - 6 + 5 + 62 + 5)^6$	$:= (18 + 3 + 82 - 65 - 6 - 2 + 5)^6$
$:= (18 + 3 + 8 - 2 - 6 - 5 - 6 + 25)^6$	$:= (18 + 3 + 82 - 6 + 5 - 62 - 5)^6$
$:= (18 + 3 - 8 + 2 + 6 - 5 - 6 + 25)^6$	$:= (18 + 3 + 82 - 6 - 5 - 62 + 5)^6$
$:= (18 - 3 - 8 - 2 + 6 + 5 - 6 + 25)^6$	$:= (-18 + 3 + 82 - 6 + 5 - 6 - 25)^6$
$:= (18 + 3 - 8 + 2 - 6 - 5 + 6 + 25)^6$	$:= (18 - 3 + 8 + 26 + 5 + 6 - 25)^6$
$:= (18 - 3 - 8 - 2 - 6 + 5 + 6 + 25)^6$	$:= (18 + 3 + 8 - 2 + 65 - 62 + 5)^6$
$:= (-1 + 83 + 8 + 2 + 6 - 56 - 2 - 5)^6$	$:= (-18 - 3 + 8 + 2 + 65 + 6 - 25)^6$
$:= (-1 + 83 + 8 - 2 + 6 - 56 + 2 - 5)^6$	$:= (-1 + 83 - 8 - 2 - 6 - 56 + 25)^6$
$:= (1 + 83 + 8 + 2 - 6 - 56 - 2 + 5)^6$	$:= (-1 + 8 + 38 + 26 - 5 - 6 - 25)^6$
$:= (1 + 83 + 8 - 2 - 6 - 56 + 2 + 5)^6$	$:= (1 + 8 + 38 - 26 - 5 - 6 + 25)^6$
$:= (1 + 83 - 8 + 2 + 6 - 56 + 2 + 5)^6$	$:= (-1 + 8 + 38 - 2 - 65 + 62 - 5)^6$
$:= (1 + 8 + 38 - 26 + 5 + 6 - 2 + 5)^6$	$:= (-1 - 8 + 38 - 2 + 65 - 62 + 5)^6$
$:= (-1 + 8 - 38 + 2 + 65 + 6 - 2 - 5)^6$	$:= (1 - 8 + 38 + 2 - 65 + 62 + 5)^6$
$:= (-1 + 8 - 38 - 2 + 65 + 6 + 2 - 5)^6$	$:= (-1 - 8 - 38 - 2 + 65 - 6 + 25)^6$
$:= (1 + 8 - 38 + 2 + 65 - 6 - 2 + 5)^6$	$:= (1 - 8 - 3 + 82 - 6 - 56 + 25)^6$
$:= (1 + 8 - 38 - 2 + 65 - 6 + 2 + 5)^6$	$:= (-1 - 8 - 3 - 8 - 26 + 56 + 25)^6$
$:= (1 - 8 - 38 + 2 + 65 + 6 + 2 + 5)^6$	$:= (183 - 82 - 65 + 6 - 2 - 5)^6$
$:= (-1 + 8 - 38 - 2 + 6 + 5 + 62 - 5)^6$	$:= (183 - 82 + 6 - 5 - 62 - 5)^6$
$:= (-1 + 8 - 38 - 2 + 6 - 5 + 62 + 5)^6$	$:= (-18 + 3 - 82 + 65 + 62 + 5)^6$
$:= (1 + 8 - 38 - 2 - 6 + 5 + 62 + 5)^6$	$:= (18 + 3 - 82 + 65 + 6 + 25)^6$
$:= (1 - 8 - 38 + 2 + 6 + 5 + 62 + 5)^6$	$:= (-1 - 83 + 82 + 6 + 56 - 25)^6$
$:= (-1 + 8 + 38 - 2 + 6 + 5 + 6 - 25)^6$	$:= (-1 + 83 + 8 + 26 - 56 - 25)^6$
$:= (-1 - 8 + 38 - 2 - 6 - 5 - 6 + 25)^6$	$:= (1 + 83 + 8 - 26 - 56 + 25)^6$
$:= (-1 + 8 + 3 + 82 + 6 - 56 - 2 - 5)^6$	$:= (18 - 38 - 26 + 56 + 25)^6$
$:= (1 + 8 - 3 + 82 + 6 - 56 + 2 - 5)^6$	1849430025 $:= (1 - 8 - 4 + 9 + 43002 + 5)^2$
$:= (1 + 8 + 3 + 82 - 6 - 56 - 2 + 5)^6$	1871773696 $:= (187 + 1 + 7 + 7 - 3 + 6 + 9 - 6)^4$
$:= (1 - 8 + 3 + 82 + 6 - 56 + 2 + 5)^6$	$:= (187 + 1 + 7 + 7 + 3 + 6 - 9 + 6)^4$
$:= (-1 + 8 - 3 + 8 - 26 + 56 - 2 - 5)^6$	$:= (187 + 1 + 7 + 7 - 3 - 6 + 9 + 6)^4$
$:= (-1 + 8 + 3 - 8 - 26 + 56 - 2 + 5)^6$	$:= (1 + 87 + 1 + 7 + 7 + 3 + 6 + 96)^4$
$:= (-1 - 8 + 3 + 8 - 26 + 56 - 2 + 5)^6$	$:= (18 + 71 + 7 + 7 + 3 + 6 + 96)^4$
$:= (1 + 8 - 3 - 8 - 26 + 56 + 2 + 5)^6$	$:= (18 + 7 + 177 - 3 + 6 + 9 - 6)^4$
$:= (1 - 8 - 3 + 8 - 26 + 56 + 2 + 5)^6$	$:= (18 + 7 + 177 + 3 + 6 - 9 + 6)^4$
$:= (-1 + 8 - 3 + 8 - 2 - 6 + 56 - 25)^6$	$:= (18 + 7 + 177 - 3 - 6 + 9 + 6)^4$
$:= (-1 + 8 - 3 - 8 + 2 + 6 + 56 - 25)^6$	$:= (18 + 7 + 1 + 77 + 3 + 6 + 96)^4$
$:= (-1 - 8 - 3 + 8 + 2 + 6 + 56 - 25)^6$	$:= (18 + 7 + 1 + 7 + 73 + 6 + 96)^4$
$:= (18 - 38 + 2 - 6 + 56 - 2 + 5)^6$	$:= (1 + 8 + 71 + 77 + 36 + 9 + 6)^4$

$:= (-1 - 8 + 71 + 7 + 7 + 36 + 96)^4$	$:= (1 + 9 + 34 + 9 + 1 + 7 + 6 + 3 + 2)^5$
$:= (-1 - 8 + 7 + 177 + 36 - 9 + 6)^4$	$:= (1 - 9 + 3 + 4 + 91 - 7 - 6 - 3 - 2)^5$
$:= (1 + 8 + 7 + 17 + 73 + 6 + 96)^4$	$:= (1 - 9 - 3 - 4 + 91 + 7 - 6 - 3 - 2)^5$
$:= (-1 + 8 - 7 - 1 + 77 + 36 + 96)^4$	$:= (1 - 9 - 3 + 4 + 91 - 7 - 6 + 3 - 2)^5$
$:= (1 - 8 + 7 - 1 + 77 + 36 + 96)^4$	$:= (-1 - 9 - 3 - 4 + 91 - 7 + 6 - 3 + 2)^5$
$:= (-1 - 8 + 7 + 1 + 77 + 36 + 96)^4$	$:= (-1 - 9 + 3 - 4 + 91 - 7 - 6 + 3 + 2)^5$
$:= (187 - 1 - 77 - 3 + 6 + 96)^4$	$:= (1 + 9 - 3 + 4 - 9 - 1 + 76 - 3 - 2)^5$
$:= (187 - 1 - 7 - 73 + 6 + 96)^4$	$:= (1 - 9 - 3 + 4 + 9 - 1 + 76 - 3 - 2)^5$
$:= (-18 + 71 + 77 + 3 + 69 + 6)^4$	$:= (1 + 9 + 3 - 4 - 9 + 1 + 76 - 3 - 2)^5$
$:= (-18 + 71 + 7 + 73 + 69 + 6)^4$	$:= (-1 + 9 - 3 + 4 - 9 + 1 + 76 - 3 - 2)^5$
$:= (-1 + 87 - 17 + 7 + 36 + 96)^4$	$:= (1 - 9 + 3 - 4 + 9 + 1 + 76 - 3 - 2)^5$
$:= (1 - 8 - 71 - 77 + 369 - 6)^4$	$:= (-1 - 9 - 3 + 4 + 9 + 1 + 76 - 3 - 2)^5$
1874516337 $:= (1 + 874 + 5 + 16 + 337)^3$	$:= (1 + 9 - 3 - 4 - 9 + 1 + 76 + 3 - 2)^5$
1883652875 $:= (1883 - 652 - 8 + 7 + 5)^3$	$:= (1 - 9 - 3 - 4 + 9 + 1 + 76 + 3 - 2)^5$
1884341281 $:= (-18 + 8 + 43412 + 8 - 1)^2$	$:= (-1 + 9 + 3 - 4 - 9 - 1 + 76 - 3 + 2)^5$
1897413272 $:= (-1 - 89 + 7 - 4 + 1327 - 2)^3$	$:= (-1 - 9 + 3 - 4 + 9 - 1 + 76 - 3 + 2)^5$
$:= (1 - 89 - 7 + 4 + 1327 + 2)^3$	$:= (-1 + 9 - 3 - 4 - 9 - 1 + 76 + 3 + 2)^5$
1904362321 $:= (19 + 043623 - 2 - 1)^2$	$:= (-1 - 9 - 3 - 4 + 9 - 1 + 76 + 3 + 2)^5$
1908029761 $:= (190 + 8 + 02 + 9 + 7 - 6 - 1)^4$	$:= (1 - 9 + 3 + 4 - 9 + 1 + 76 + 3 + 2)^5$
$:= (190 + 8 + 02 + 9 - 7 + 6 + 1)^4$	$:= (1 + 9 + 3 + 4 + 9 + 1 + 7 + 6 + 32)^5$
$:= (190 - 8 + 029 - 7 + 6 - 1)^4$	$:= (19 - 3 + 49 - 1 + 7 + 6 - 3 - 2)^5$
$:= (1 - 90 + 8 + 0297 - 6 - 1)^4$	$:= (19 + 3 + 49 - 1 + 7 - 6 + 3 - 2)^5$
$:= (-1 - 90 + 8 + 0297 - 6 + 1)^4$	$:= (19 + 3 + 49 + 1 - 7 + 6 + 3 - 2)^5$
$:= (190 + 80 - 2 + 9 - 7 - 61)^4$	$:= (19 + 3 + 49 + 1 + 7 - 6 - 3 + 2)^5$
$:= (190 + 80 + 2 - 9 + 7 - 61)^4$	$:= (19 - 3 + 49 + 1 + 7 - 6 + 3 + 2)^5$
$:= (-19 - 08 + 0297 - 61)^4$	$:= (19 + 3 + 4 - 9 + 1 - 7 + 63 - 2)^5$
$:= (1 + 90 + 80 + 2 + 97 - 61)^4$	$:= (19 - 3 - 4 - 9 + 1 + 7 + 63 - 2)^5$
1909427809 $:= (-1 + 909 + 42780 + 9)^2$	$:= (1 - 9 + 34 - 9 + 1 - 7 + 63 - 2)^5$
1911240521 $:= (1 + 9 - 1 + 1240 - 5 - 2 - 1)^3$	$:= (-1 - 9 + 34 - 9 - 1 - 7 + 63 + 2)^5$
$:= (-1 + 9 + 1 + 1240 - 5 - 2 - 1)^3$	$:= (-1 + 9 - 3 + 49 + 17 + 6 - 3 - 2)^5$
$:= (-1 + 9 - 1 + 1240 - 5 - 2 + 1)^3$	$:= (-1 + 9 + 3 + 49 + 17 - 6 + 3 - 2)^5$
$:= (1 - 9 + 1 + 1240 + 5 + 2 + 1)^3$	$:= (1 + 9 + 3 + 49 + 17 - 6 - 3 + 2)^5$
1925134784 $:= (-192 + 5 + 1347 + 84)^3$	$:= (1 + 9 - 3 + 49 + 17 - 6 + 3 + 2)^5$
1934917632 $:= (1 + 93 + 4 - 9 + 1 - 7 - 6 - 3 - 2)^5$	$:= (1 - 9 + 3 + 49 + 17 + 6 + 3 + 2)^5$
$:= (-1 + 93 - 4 - 9 - 1 - 7 + 6 - 3 - 2)^5$	$:= (-1 + 9 - 3 + 49 - 1 - 7 - 6 + 32)^5$
$:= (-1 + 93 + 4 - 9 - 1 - 7 - 6 - 3 + 2)^5$	$:= (1 - 9 - 3 + 49 + 1 + 7 - 6 + 32)^5$
$:= (1 + 93 - 4 - 9 - 1 - 7 - 6 + 3 + 2)^5$	$:= (-1 - 9 + 3 + 49 - 1 - 7 + 6 + 32)^5$
$:= (-1 + 93 - 4 - 9 + 1 - 7 - 6 + 3 + 2)^5$	$:= (1 + 9 - 3 - 4 - 9 + 17 + 63 - 2)^5$

$$\begin{aligned} &:= (1 - 9 - 3 - 4 + 9 + 17 + 63 - 2)^5 \\ &:= (-1 + 9 + 3 + 4 + 9 - 17 + 63 + 2)^5 \\ &:= (1 - 9 + 3 + 4 - 9 + 17 + 63 + 2)^5 \\ &:= (19 - 34 + 91 + 7 - 6 - 3 - 2)^5 \\ &:= (19 + 34 + 9 + 17 - 6 - 3 + 2)^5 \\ &:= (19 + 34 - 9 + 17 + 6 + 3 + 2)^5 \\ &:= (19 - 34 + 9 + 1 + 76 + 3 - 2)^5 \\ &:= (19 + 3 + 4 + 91 - 7 - 6 - 32)^5 \\ &:= (19 - 3 - 4 + 91 + 7 - 6 - 32)^5 \\ &:= (19 - 3 + 4 + 9 + 17 - 6 + 32)^5 \\ &:= (19 + 3 + 4 - 9 + 17 + 6 + 32)^5 \\ &:= (19 - 3 + 4 + 9 - 1 + 76 - 32)^5 \\ &:= (19 + 3 - 4 + 9 + 1 + 76 - 32)^5 \\ &:= (-19 - 3 - 4 - 9 - 1 + 76 + 32)^5 \\ &:= (1 + 93 + 49 + 1 - 7 - 63 - 2)^5 \\ &:= (-1 + 93 + 49 - 1 - 7 - 63 + 2)^5 \\ &:= (-1 - 93 + 4 + 91 + 76 - 3 - 2)^5 \\ &:= (1 - 93 - 4 + 91 + 76 + 3 - 2)^5 \\ &:= (-1 + 93 - 4 - 91 + 76 - 3 + 2)^5 \\ &:= (-1 - 93 + 4 - 9 + 176 - 3 - 2)^5 \\ &:= (1 - 93 - 4 - 9 + 176 + 3 - 2)^5 \\ &:= (1 + 93 - 4 - 9 + 17 + 6 - 32)^5 \\ &:= (1 - 9 + 34 + 91 - 7 - 6 - 32)^5 \\ &:= (-1 + 9 + 34 + 9 - 17 + 6 + 32)^5 \\ &:= (1 - 9 + 34 - 9 + 17 + 6 + 32)^5 \\ &:= (-1 + 9 - 34 - 9 - 1 + 76 + 32)^5 \\ &:= (-1 - 9 - 34 + 9 - 1 + 76 + 32)^5 \\ &:= (193 - 49 - 1 - 76 + 3 + 2)^5 \\ &:= (19 + 34 + 91 - 7 - 63 - 2)^5 \\ &:= (19 - 34 + 9 + 17 + 63 - 2)^5 \\ &:= (-19 + 34 + 9 - 17 + 63 + 2)^5 \\ &:= (-19 - 3 + 49 + 1 + 76 - 32)^5 \end{aligned}$$

$$\mathbf{1944016281} := (1 - 9 + 44016 + 2 + 81)^2$$

$$\mathbf{1944104464} := (-1 - 9 + 44104 - 4 + 6 - 4)^2$$

$$\mathbf{1953125000} := (-1 + 9 - 5 - 3 + 1250 + 00)^3 \\ := (1 - 9 + 5 + 3 + 1250 + 00)^3$$

$$\mathbf{1959744361} := (1 - 95 + 9 - 7 + 44361)^2 \\ := (1 + 9 - 5 - 97 + 44361)^2$$

$$\mathbf{1967221277} := (-19 + 6 - 7 - 2 - 2 + 1277)^3 \\ := (-1 + 967 - 2 + 212 + 77)^3$$

$$\mathbf{1977326743} := (-1 + 9 + 7 + 7 + 3 + 2 - 6 - 7 - 4 - 3)^{11} \\ := (1 + 9 + 7 - 7 + 3 + 2 + 6 - 7 - 4 - 3)^{11} \\ := (1 + 9 - 7 + 7 + 3 + 2 + 6 - 7 - 4 - 3)^{11} \\ := (-1 + 9 + 7 - 7 + 3 + 2 - 6 + 7 - 4 - 3)^{11} \\ := (-1 + 9 - 7 + 7 + 3 + 2 - 6 + 7 - 4 - 3)^{11} \\ := (1 - 9 + 7 + 7 - 3 - 2 + 6 + 7 - 4 - 3)^{11} \\ := (1 + 9 - 7 - 7 + 3 + 2 + 6 + 7 - 4 - 3)^{11} \\ := (1 + 9 + 7 + 7 - 3 - 2 - 6 - 7 + 4 - 3)^{11} \\ := (1 - 9 + 7 + 7 + 3 - 2 + 6 - 7 + 4 - 3)^{11} \\ := (-1 + 9 + 7 - 7 - 3 + 2 + 6 - 7 + 4 - 3)^{11} \\ := (-1 + 9 - 7 + 7 - 3 + 2 + 6 - 7 + 4 - 3)^{11} \\ := (1 + 9 + 7 - 7 - 3 - 2 - 6 + 7 + 4 - 3)^{11} \\ := (1 + 9 - 7 + 7 - 3 - 2 - 6 + 7 + 4 - 3)^{11} \\ := (-1 - 9 + 7 + 7 + 3 - 2 - 6 + 7 + 4 - 3)^{11} \\ := (1 - 9 + 7 + 7 - 3 + 2 - 6 + 7 + 4 - 3)^{11} \\ := (1 - 9 + 7 - 7 + 3 - 2 + 6 + 7 + 4 - 3)^{11} \\ := (1 - 9 - 7 + 7 + 3 - 2 + 6 + 7 + 4 - 3)^{11} \\ := (-1 + 9 - 7 - 7 - 3 + 2 + 6 + 7 + 4 - 3)^{11} \\ := (-1 + 9 + 7 + 7 - 3 + 2 - 6 - 7 - 4 + 3)^{11} \\ := (-1 + 9 + 7 - 7 + 3 - 2 + 6 - 7 - 4 + 3)^{11} \\ := (-1 + 9 - 7 + 7 + 3 - 2 + 6 - 7 - 4 + 3)^{11} \\ := (1 + 9 + 7 - 7 - 3 + 2 + 6 - 7 - 4 + 3)^{11} \\ := (1 + 9 - 7 + 7 - 3 + 2 + 6 - 7 - 4 + 3)^{11} \\ := (-1 - 9 + 7 + 7 + 3 + 2 + 6 - 7 - 4 + 3)^{11} \\ := (1 - 9 + 7 + 7 + 3 - 2 - 6 + 7 - 4 + 3)^{11} \\ := (-1 + 9 + 7 - 7 - 3 + 2 - 6 + 7 - 4 + 3)^{11} \\ := (-1 + 9 - 7 + 7 + 3 + 2 - 6 - 7 + 4 + 3)^{11} \\ := (-1 + 9 - 7 + 7 + 3 + 2 - 6 - 7 + 4 + 3)^{11} \\ := (1 - 9 + 7 + 7 - 3 - 2 + 6 - 7 + 4 + 3)^{11} \\ := (1 + 9 - 7 - 7 + 3 + 2 + 6 - 7 + 4 + 3)^{11} \\ := (-1 - 9 + 7 + 7 + 3 + 2 + 6 - 7 - 4 + 3)^{11} \\ := (1 - 9 + 7 + 7 + 3 - 2 - 6 + 7 - 4 + 3)^{11} \\ := (-1 + 9 + 7 - 7 + 3 + 2 - 6 - 7 + 4 + 3)^{11} \\ := (-1 + 9 - 7 + 7 + 3 + 2 - 6 - 7 + 4 + 3)^{11} \\ := (1 - 9 + 7 + 7 - 3 - 2 + 6 - 7 + 4 + 3)^{11} \\ := (1 + 9 - 7 - 7 + 3 + 2 + 6 - 7 + 4 + 3)^{11} \\ := (-1 - 9 + 7 + 7 - 3 - 2 - 6 + 7 + 4 + 3)^{11}$$

$$\begin{aligned} & := (-1+9-7-7+3+2-6+7+4+3)^{11} & := (-1+9+7+73+2-6-74-3)^{11} \\ & := (1-9+7-7-3-2+6+7+4+3)^{11} & := (1+9-7+73+2+6-74-3)^{11} \\ & := (1-9-7+7-3-2+6+7+4+3)^{11} & := (1+9+7-73-2-6+74-3)^{11} \\ & := (1-9+7-7+3+26-7-4-3)^{11} & := (-1+9-7-73+2+6+74-3)^{11} \\ & := (1-9-7+7+3+26-7-4-3)^{11} & := (-1+9-7+73-2+6-74+3)^{11} \\ & := (1-9-7-7+3+26+7-4-3)^{11} & := (-1-9+7+73+2+6-74+3)^{11} \\ & := (-1-9+7-7-3+26-7+4-3)^{11} & := (1-9+7-73-2+6+74+3)^{11} \\ & := (-1-9-7+7-3+26-7+4-3)^{11} & := (-1+9-7-7+3-26-7+43)^{11} \\ & := (-1+9+7+7+3-26+7+4-3)^{11} & := (1-9-7-7+3+2+67-43)^{11} \\ & := (-1-9-7-7-3+26+7+4-3)^{11} & := (19-77+3+2+67-4-3)^{11} \\ & := (1-9+7-7-3+26-7-4+3)^{11} & := (19-77-3+2+67-4+3)^{11} \\ & := (1-9-7+7-3+26-7-4+3)^{11} & := (-19+77+3+2-6-7-43)^{11} \\ & := (1+9+7+7+3-26+7-4+3)^{11} & := (-19-7+73-26-7-4-3)^{11} \\ & := (1-9-7-7-3+26+7-4+3)^{11} & := (19-7-73+2+67-4+3)^{11} \\ & := (1-9-7-7+3+26-7+4+3)^{11} & := (-19+7+73+2-6-7-43)^{11} \\ & := (-1+9+7+7-3-26+7+4+3)^{11} & := (-19-7+73+2-6+7-43)^{11} \\ & := (-1-9-7-7+3-2-6-7+43)^{11} & := (19+7-73-2+6+7+43)^{11} \\ & := (1-9-7-7-3+2-6-7+43)^{11} & := (19+7-7+32+6-7-43)^{11} \\ & := (-19+7+7+32-6-7-4-3)^{11} & := (19-7+7+32+6-7-43)^{11} \\ & := (-19+7-7+32-6+7-4-3)^{11} & := (19-7-7+32+6+7-43)^{11} \\ & := (-19-7+7+32-6+7-4-3)^{11} & := (-19+7+7-32-6+7+43)^{11} \\ & := (19+7+7-32+6+7-4-3)^{11} & := (1+97-73-26+7+4-3)^{11} \\ & := (-19+7-7+32-6-7+4+3)^{11} & := (-1-97+73+26+7-4+3)^{11} \\ & := (-19-7+7+32-6-7+4+3)^{11} & := (-1-97+73+2-6-7+43)^{11} \\ & := (19+7+7-32+6-7+4+3)^{11} & := (1+97+7-32-67+4-3)^{11} \\ & := (-19-7-7+32-6+7+4+3)^{11} & := (-1-97+7+32+67-4+3)^{11} \\ & := (19+7-7-32+6+7+4+3)^{11} & := (1-9-77+32+67-4-3)^{11} \\ & := (19-7+7-32+6+7+4+3)^{11} & := (1-9+77-32+6+7-43)^{11} \\ & := (1+97-73+2-6-7-4-3)^{11} & := (1+9-77+32+6-7+43)^{11} \\ & := (-1+97-73-2-6-7-4+3)^{11} & := (-1+9-77+32-6+7+43)^{11} \\ & := (-1+97-7+3-2-6-74-3)^{11} & := (-1-9-77-3+26+74-3)^{11} \\ & := (1+97-7-3+2-6-74-3)^{11} & := (1-9-7+73+26-74-3)^{11} \\ & := (-1+97-7-3-2-6-74+3)^{11} & := (-1-9-7-73+26+74-3)^{11} \\ & := (-1+9+77+3+2-6-74-3)^{11} & := (-19+77+32-6-74-3)^{11} \\ & := (-1+9-77-3+2+6+74-3)^{11} & := (-19-77+32-6+74+3)^{11} \\ & := (-1+9+77-3+2-6-74+3)^{11} & := (19-77+3+26-7+43)^{11} \\ & := (-1-9+77+3+2+6-74+3)^{11} & := (-1+9+77+32-67-43)^{11} \\ & := (-1+9-77+3+2-6+74+3)^{11} & := (-19+773+2-6-743)^{11} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 & := (19 - 7 + 732 + 6 - 743)^{11} \\
 \mathbf{1982119441} & := (1 + 9 + 8 + 211 - 9 - 4 - 4 - 1)^4 \\
 & := (-1 + 9 - 8 + 211 + 9 - 4 - 4 - 1)^4 \\
 & := (1 - 9 + 8 + 211 + 9 - 4 - 4 - 1)^4 \\
 & := (1 + 9 - 8 + 211 - 9 + 4 + 4 - 1)^4 \\
 & := (1 - 9 - 8 + 211 + 9 + 4 + 4 - 1)^4 \\
 & := (-1 + 9 + 8 + 211 - 9 - 4 - 4 + 1)^4 \\
 & := (-1 - 9 + 8 + 211 + 9 - 4 - 4 + 1)^4 \\
 & := (-1 + 9 - 8 + 211 - 9 + 4 + 4 + 1)^4 \\
 & := (1 - 9 + 8 + 211 - 9 + 4 + 4 + 1)^4 \\
 & := (-1 - 9 - 8 + 211 + 9 + 4 + 4 + 1)^4 \\
 & := (198 + 2 + 11 + 9 - 4 - 4 - 1)^4 \\
 & := (198 + 2 + 11 - 9 + 4 + 4 + 1)^4 \\
 & := (198 + 2 + 1 + 19 - 4 - 4 - 1)^4 \\
 & := (198 + 2 - 1 + 19 - 4 - 4 + 1)^4 \\
 & := (19 - 8 + 2 + 1 + 194 + 4 - 1)^4 \\
 & := (19 - 8 + 2 - 1 + 194 + 4 + 1)^4 \\
 & := (1 + 98 + 2 + 119 - 4 - 4 - 1)^4 \\
 & := (-1 + 98 + 2 + 119 - 4 - 4 + 1)^4 \\
 & := (1 + 98 + 2 + 11 + 94 + 4 + 1)^4 \\
 & := (1 - 9 + 82 + 1 + 1 + 94 + 41)^4 \\
 & := (19 + 82 + 119 - 4 - 4 - 1)^4 \\
 & := (19 + 82 + 11 + 94 + 4 + 1)^4 \\
 & := (-19 - 8 + 2 + 1 + 194 + 41)^4 \\
 & := (1 + 98 + 211 - 94 - 4 - 1)^4 \\
 & := (1 - 98 + 211 + 94 + 4 - 1)^4 \\
 & := (-1 + 98 + 211 - 94 - 4 + 1)^4 \\
 & := (-1 - 98 + 211 + 94 + 4 + 1)^4 \\
 \mathbf{1995616979} & := (19 - 9 + 561 + 697 - 9)^3 \\
 \mathbf{2019487744} & := (2019 + 4 - 8 - 7 - 744)^3 \\
 \mathbf{2019963136} & := (201 + 9 + 9 + 6 - 3 - 1 - 3 - 6)^4 \\
 & := (201 + 9 + 9 - 6 + 3 - 1 + 3 - 6)^4 \\
 & := (201 + 9 + 9 - 6 - 3 - 1 - 3 + 6)^4 \\
 & := (201 + 9 - 9 + 6 + 3 - 1 - 3 + 6)^4 \\
 & := (201 - 9 + 9 + 6 + 3 - 1 - 3 + 6)^4 \\
 & := (201 + 9 - 9 + 6 - 3 - 1 + 3 + 6)^4 \\
 & := (201 - 9 + 9 + 6 - 3 - 1 + 3 + 6)^4 \\
 & := (2 + 0199 + 6 + 3 - 1 - 3 + 6)^4 \\
 & := (2 + 0199 + 6 - 3 - 1 + 3 + 6)^4 \\
 & := (20 + 199 + 6 - 3 - 1 - 3 - 6)^4 \\
 & := (20 + 199 - 6 + 3 - 1 + 3 - 6)^4 \\
 & := (20 + 199 - 6 - 3 - 1 - 3 + 6)^4 \\
 & := (201 + 9 - 9 + 6 - 31 + 36)^4 \\
 & := (201 - 9 + 9 + 6 - 31 + 36)^4 \\
 & := (2 + 0199 + 6 - 31 + 36)^4 \\
 & := (2 - 019 + 96 - 3 + 136)^4 \\
 & := (20 - 19 - 96 + 313 - 6)^4 \\
 \mathbf{2033901163} & := (20 - 3 - 3 + 90 + 1163)^3 \\
 \mathbf{2045210176} & := (2 + 045210 - 1 + 7 + 6)^2 \\
 \mathbf{2058346161} & := (205 - 8 + 3 + 4 - 6 + 16 - 1)^4 \\
 & := (205 - 8 - 3 - 4 + 6 + 16 + 1)^4 \\
 & := (20 - 5 + 83 - 46 + 161)^4 \\
 \mathbf{2073071593} & := (2 + 073 + 07 - 15 + 9 - 3)^5 \\
 & := (-2 + 073 - 07 + 15 - 9 + 3)^5 \\
 & := (2 + 07 + 30 + 7 + 15 + 9 + 3)^5 \\
 & := (2 - 07 + 30 - 7 - 1 + 59 - 3)^5 \\
 & := (2 + 07 - 30 + 7 - 1 - 5 + 93)^5 \\
 & := (-2 + 07 - 3 - 07 - 15 + 93)^5 \\
 & := (-2 - 07 - 3 + 07 - 15 + 93)^5 \\
 & := (20 + 73 + 07 - 15 - 9 - 3)^5 \\
 & := (-20 + 73 - 07 + 15 + 9 + 3)^5 \\
 & := (-20 - 7 + 30 + 71 + 5 - 9 + 3)^5 \\
 & := (20 + 7 + 30 + 7 + 15 - 9 + 3)^5 \\
 & := (-20 + 7 + 30 - 7 + 1 + 59 + 3)^5 \\
 & := (-20 - 7 + 30 + 7 + 1 + 59 + 3)^5 \\
 & := (20 - 7 - 30 - 7 - 1 + 5 + 93)^5 \\
 & := (207 - 30 - 7 + 1 - 5 - 93)^5 \\
 & := (-207 + 307 - 15 - 9 - 3)^5 \\
 \mathbf{2084561649} & := (20 + 8 + 45616 + 4 + 9)^2 \\
 \mathbf{2097273616} & := (209 + 7 - 2 + 7 + 3 + 6 - 16)^4 \\
 & := (209 + 7 - 2 - 7 - 3 - 6 + 16)^4 \\
 & := (209 - 7 - 2 + 7 - 3 - 6 + 16)^4 \\
 & := (-2 - 09 + 7 + 273 - 61 + 6)^4 \\
 & := (209 - 72 + 7 + 3 + 61 + 6)^4 \\
 & := (209 + 7 + 27 - 36 + 1 + 6)^4 \\
 & := (209 + 7 - 27 + 3 + 6 + 16)^4
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 &:= (20 + 97 + 27 + 3 + 61 + 6)^4 & &:= (-2 + 1 + 47 - 4 + 8 - 36 - 4 - 8)^{31} \\
 &:= (20 + 97 + 2 + 73 + 6 + 16)^4 & &:= (-2 + 1 + 47 + 4 - 8 - 36 + 4 - 8)^{31} \\
 &:= (-20 + 9 + 7 + 273 - 61 + 6)^4 & &:= (-2 + 1 + 47 - 4 - 8 - 36 - 4 + 8)^{31} \\
 \mathbf{2104607376} &:= (-210 + 46073 + 7 + 6)^2 & &:= (-2 - 1 - 47 + 4 + 8 + 36 - 4 + 8)^{31} \\
 \mathbf{2116460025} &:= (2 + 1 - 1 + 6 + 46002 - 5)^2 & &:= (-2 - 1 - 47 - 4 + 8 + 36 + 4 + 8)^{31} \\
 &:= (2 - 1 + 1 + 6 + 46002 - 5)^2 & &:= (2 + 1 - 4 - 74 + 83 + 6 - 4 - 8)^{31} \\
 &:= (2 + 1 + 1 - 6 + 46002 + 5)^2 & &:= (-2 + 1 + 4 - 74 + 83 - 6 + 4 - 8)^{31} \\
 \mathbf{2126781656} &:= (2126 - 781 - 65 + 6)^3 & &:= (-2 + 1 - 4 - 74 + 83 - 6 - 4 + 8)^{31} \\
 \mathbf{2131746903} &:= (21 + 317 + 46 + 903)^3 & &:= (-2 - 1 + 4 + 74 - 83 + 6 - 4 + 8)^{31} \\
 \mathbf{2136719872} &:= (2 + 1367 - 1 + 9 - 87 - 2)^3 & &:= (2 - 1 + 4 + 74 - 83 - 6 + 4 + 8)^{31} \\
 &:= (-2 + 1367 - 1 + 9 - 87 + 2)^3 & &:= (-2 - 1 - 4 + 74 - 83 + 6 + 4 + 8)^{31} \\
 \mathbf{2136750625} &:= (213 - 6 + 75 - 062 - 5)^4 & &:= (-2 + 1 - 4 + 74 + 8 - 3 - 64 - 8)^{31} \\
 &:= (213 - 67 + 50 - 6 + 25)^4 & &:= (2 - 1 + 4 + 74 - 8 + 3 - 64 - 8)^{31} \\
 \mathbf{2141700569} &:= (-21 + 41 + 700 + 569)^3 & &:= (-2 + 1 - 4 + 74 - 8 - 3 - 64 + 8)^{31} \\
 \mathbf{2141745841} &:= (21 + 417 + 45841)^2 & &:= (2 + 1 - 4 - 74 + 8 - 3 + 64 + 8)^{31} \\
 \mathbf{2147483648} &:= (-2 + 14 + 7 - 4 + 8 - 3 - 6 - 4 - 8)^{31} & &:= (-2 - 1 - 4 - 74 + 8 + 3 + 64 + 8)^{31} \\
 &:= (-2 + 14 - 7 + 4 + 8 + 3 - 6 - 4 - 8)^{31} & &:= (-2 - 1 - 4 + 74 - 8 - 3 - 6 - 48)^{31} \\
 &:= (2 + 14 + 7 - 4 - 8 - 3 + 6 - 4 - 8)^{31} & &:= (-2 + 1 - 4 + 7 + 48 - 36 - 4 - 8)^{31} \\
 &:= (2 + 14 - 7 + 4 - 8 + 3 + 6 - 4 - 8)^{31} & &:= (-2 - 1 + 4 - 7 + 48 - 36 + 4 - 8)^{31} \\
 &:= (-2 + 14 + 7 + 4 - 8 - 3 - 6 + 4 - 8)^{31} & &:= (-2 - 1 - 4 - 7 + 48 - 36 - 4 + 8)^{31} \\
 &:= (-2 + 14 - 7 - 4 + 8 + 3 - 6 + 4 - 8)^{31} & &:= (-2 + 1 + 4 + 7 - 48 + 36 - 4 + 8)^{31} \\
 &:= (-2 - 14 + 7 + 4 + 8 - 3 + 6 + 4 - 8)^{31} & &:= (-2 + 1 - 4 + 7 - 48 + 36 + 4 + 8)^{31} \\
 &:= (2 + 14 - 7 - 4 - 8 + 3 + 6 + 4 - 8)^{31} & &:= (-2 + 1 + 4 + 7 - 4 + 8 + 36 - 48)^{31} \\
 &:= (-2 + 14 + 7 - 4 - 8 - 3 - 6 - 4 + 8)^{31} & &:= (-2 + 1 - 4 + 7 + 4 + 8 + 36 - 48)^{31} \\
 &:= (2 - 14 + 7 + 4 + 8 - 3 - 6 - 4 + 8)^{31} & &:= (-2 + 1 - 4 + 7 - 4 - 8 - 36 + 48)^{31} \\
 &:= (-2 + 14 - 7 + 4 - 8 + 3 - 6 - 4 + 8)^{31} & &:= (-2 - 1 + 4 - 7 + 4 - 8 - 36 + 48)^{31} \\
 &:= (-2 - 14 + 7 - 4 + 8 - 3 + 6 - 4 + 8)^{31} & &:= (-2 - 1 - 4 - 7 - 4 + 8 - 36 + 48)^{31} \\
 &:= (-2 - 14 - 7 + 4 + 8 + 3 + 6 - 4 + 8)^{31} & &:= (21 - 47 - 4 + 8 + 36 - 4 - 8)^{31} \\
 &:= (2 - 14 + 7 - 4 + 8 - 3 - 6 + 4 + 8)^{31} & &:= (21 - 47 + 4 - 8 + 36 + 4 - 8)^{31} \\
 &:= (-2 + 14 - 7 - 4 - 8 + 3 - 6 + 4 + 8)^{31} & &:= (21 - 47 - 4 - 8 + 36 - 4 + 8)^{31} \\
 &:= (2 - 14 - 7 + 4 + 8 + 3 - 6 + 4 + 8)^{31} & &:= (21 - 4 + 74 - 83 + 6 - 4 - 8)^{31} \\
 &:= (-2 - 14 + 7 + 4 - 8 - 3 + 6 + 4 + 8)^{31} & &:= (-21 + 4 - 74 + 83 + 6 - 4 + 8)^{31} \\
 &:= (-2 - 14 - 7 - 4 + 8 + 3 + 6 + 4 + 8)^{31} & &:= (-21 - 4 - 74 + 83 + 6 + 4 + 8)^{31} \\
 &:= (2 - 1 - 4 - 7 - 4 - 8 + 36 - 4 - 8)^{31} & &:= (21 + 4 - 74 - 8 + 3 + 64 - 8)^{31} \\
 &:= (2 + 1 + 4 + 7 + 4 + 8 - 36 + 4 + 8)^{31} & &:= (-21 - 4 + 74 - 8 + 3 + 6 - 48)^{31} \\
 &:= (-21 + 4 + 7 - 4 - 8 + 36 - 4 - 8)^{31} & &:= (21 - 4 - 74 + 8 - 3 + 6 + 48)^{31} \\
 &:= (-21 - 4 + 7 + 4 - 8 + 36 - 4 - 8)^{31} & &:= (21 + 4 - 7 - 48 + 36 + 4 - 8)^{31} \\
 &:= (-21 - 4 + 7 - 4 - 8 + 36 + 4 - 8)^{31} & &:= (21 - 4 - 7 - 48 + 36 - 4 + 8)^{31}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 &:= (21+4-7+4-8+36-48)^{31} \\
 &:= (21-4-7-4+8+36-48)^{31} \\
 &:= (-2-14+74-8-36-4-8)^{31} \\
 &:= (2+14+7+48+3-64-8)^{31} \\
 &:= (-2-14+7-48+3+64-8)^{31} \\
 &:= (2-14-7-48-3+64+8)^{31} \\
 &:= (-2+14-7+48+3-6-48)^{31} \\
 &:= (-2+14-7-48+3-6+48)^{31} \\
 &:= (2-14+7-4+83-64-8)^{31} \\
 &:= (2+14-7+4-83+64+8)^{31} \\
 &:= (-2-14-7-4+83-6-48)^{31} \\
 &:= (-21+47-48+36-4-8)^{31} \\
 &:= (-21+47-4-8+36-48)^{31} \\
 &:= (-2+147-4-83-64+8)^{31} \\
 &:= (-2-147-4+83+64+8)^{31} \\
 &:= (-2-14-74+8+36+48)^{31} \\
 \mathbf{2171747375} &:= (2+171+747+375)^3 \\
 \mathbf{2176782336} &:= (-2+17+6+7-8-2-3-3-6)^{12} \\
 &:= (2+17-6-7+8-2+3-3-6)^{12} \\
 &:= (2+17+6-7-8+2+3-3-6)^{12} \\
 &:= (-2+17-6-7+8+2+3-3-6)^{12} \\
 &:= (2+17+6+7+8+2+3-3-6)^6 \\
 &:= (2+17-6-7+8-2-3+3-6)^{12} \\
 &:= (2+17+6-7-8+2-3+3-6)^{12} \\
 &:= (-2+17-6-7+8+2-3+3-6)^{12} \\
 &:= (2+17+6+7+8+2-3+3-6)^6 \\
 &:= (-2+17-6+7-8-2+3+3-6)^{12} \\
 &:= (-2+17-6+7-8-2-3-3+6)^{12} \\
 &:= (-2-17+6+7+8-2+3-3+6)^{12} \\
 &:= (2+17-6-7-8+2+3-3+6)^{12} \\
 &:= (2+17-6+7+8+2+3-3+6)^6 \\
 &:= (-2-17+6+7+8-2-3+3+6)^{12} \\
 &:= (2+17-6-7-8+2-3+3+6)^{12} \\
 &:= (2+17-6+7+8+2-3+3+6)^6 \\
 &:= (2+17+6-7+8-2+3+3+6)^6 \\
 &:= (2-17+6-7+8+2+3+3+6)^{12} \\
 &:= (-2+17+6-7+8+2+3+3+6)^6 \\
 &:= (-2-1-7+6-7-8-2+33-6)^{12}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 &:= (-2+1+7+6+7-8-2+33-6)^6 \\
 &:= (-2-1+7+6-7+8-2+33-6)^6 \\
 &:= (-2-1-7+6+7+8-2+33-6)^6 \\
 &:= (2+1+7+6+7+8+2-33+6)^{12} \\
 &:= (-2-1-7-6-7-8-2+33+6)^{12} \\
 &:= (2-1+7+6-7-8-2+33+6)^6 \\
 &:= (-2+1+7-6+7-8-2+33+6)^6 \\
 &:= (2-1-7+6+7-8-2+33+6)^6 \\
 &:= (-2-1+7-6-7+8-2+33+6)^6 \\
 &:= (-2+1-7+6-7+8-2+33+6)^6 \\
 &:= (-2-1-7-6+7+8-2+33+6)^6 \\
 &:= (-2-1+7+6-7-8+2+33+6)^6 \\
 &:= (-2-1-7+6+7-8+2+33+6)^6 \\
 &:= (2+1-7-6-7-8-2-3+36)^{12} \\
 &:= (2+1+7-6-7+8-2-3+36)^6 \\
 &:= (2+1-7-6+7+8-2-3+36)^6 \\
 &:= (-2+1-7-6-7-8+2-3+36)^{12} \\
 &:= (2+1+7+6-7-8+2-3+36)^6 \\
 &:= (2-1+7-6+7-8+2-3+36)^6 \\
 &:= (2+1-7+6+7-8+2-3+36)^6 \\
 &:= (-2+1+7-6-7+8+2-3+36)^6 \\
 &:= (2-1-7+6-7+8+2-3+36)^6 \\
 &:= (-2+1-7-6+7+8+2-3+36)^6 \\
 &:= (-2-1-7-6-7-8-2+3+36)^{12} \\
 &:= (2-1+7+6-7-8-2+3+36)^6 \\
 &:= (-2+1+7-6+7-8-2+3+36)^6 \\
 &:= (2-1-7+6+7-8-2+3+36)^6 \\
 &:= (-2-1+7-6-7+8-2+3+36)^6 \\
 &:= (-2+1-7+6-7+8-2+3+36)^6 \\
 &:= (-2-1-7-6+7+8-2+3+36)^6 \\
 &:= (-2-1+7+6-7-8+2+3+36)^6 \\
 &:= (-2-1-7+6+7-8+2+3+36)^6 \\
 &:= (217-6+7+8+2-3-3-6)^4 \\
 &:= (217+6-7+8-2+3-3-6)^4 \\
 &:= (217+6-7+8-2-3+3-6)^4 \\
 &:= (217-6-7+8-2+3-3+6)^4 \\
 &:= (217+6-7-8+2+3-3+6)^4 \\
 &:= (217-6-7+8-2-3+3+6)^4
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} &:= (217+6-7-8+2-3+3+6)^4 & &:= (2-1-76-7+82+3-3+6)^{12} \\ &:= (-21+76-7-8+2+3-3-6)^6 & &:= (-2+1+76+7-82-3+3+6)^{12} \\ &:= (-21+76-7-8+2-3+3-6)^6 & &:= (2-1-76-7+82-3+3+6)^{12} \\ &:= (-21-7-6+78-2+3-3-6)^6 & &:= (2-1+76-7-8-23+3-6)^6 \\ &:= (-21-7-6+78-2-3+3-6)^6 & &:= (-2+1+7+67-8-2-33+6)^6 \\ &:= (-21+7-6-7+8-2+33-6)^{12} & &:= (-2-1-7+67+8-2-33+6)^6 \\ &:= (-21-7-6+7+8-2+33-6)^{12} & &:= (2+1-7+67+8-2+3-36)^6 \\ &:= (21+7-6-7-8+2+33-6)^6 & &:= (2-1+7+67-8+2+3-36)^6 \\ &:= (-21+7+6-7-8+2+33-6)^{12} & &:= (-2+1-7+67+8+2+3-36)^6 \\ &:= (21-7-6+7-8+2+33-6)^6 & &:= (2+1-7-6+78-23-3-6)^6 \\ &:= (-21-7+6+7-8+2+33-6)^{12} & &:= (-2-1-7-6+78-23+3-6)^6 \\ &:= (-21+7+6+7+8+2+33-6)^6 & &:= (-2+1+7-6-7+82-33-6)^6 \\ &:= (21+7+6-7+8-2-33+6)^{12} & &:= (2-1-7+6-7+82-33-6)^6 \\ &:= (21-7+6+7+8-2-33+6)^{12} & &:= (-2+1-7-6+7+82-33-6)^6 \\ &:= (-21+7-6-7-8+2+33+6)^{12} & &:= (2-1-7-6-7+82-33+6)^6 \\ &:= (-21-7-6+7-8+2+33+6)^{12} & &:= (-2+1+7-6-7+82-3-36)^6 \\ &:= (-21+7-6+7+8+2+33+6)^6 & &:= (2-1-7+6-7+82-3-36)^6 \\ &:= (21+7-6+7+8+2+3-36)^{12} & &:= (-2+1-7-6+7+82-3-36)^6 \\ &:= (21-7+6-7-8-2-3+36)^6 & &:= (2+1+7-6-7-8+233-6)^4 \\ &:= (-21+7-6-7-8+2+3+36)^{12} & &:= (2+1-7-6+7-8+233-6)^4 \\ &:= (-21-7-6+7-8+2+3+36)^{12} & &:= (2-1-7-6-7+8+233-6)^4 \\ &:= (-21+7-6+7+8+2+3+36)^6 & &:= (2+1+7-6+7+8+23-36)^{12} \\ &:= (2-17+67-8-2+3-3-6)^6 & &:= (217-6-7-8+23+3-6)^4 \\ &:= (-2-17+67-8+2+3-3-6)^6 & &:= (-21+76-7+8-23-3+6)^6 \\ &:= (2-17+67-8-2-3+3-6)^6 & &:= (-21-7+67+8-2-33-6)^{12} \\ &:= (-2-17+67-8+2-3+3-6)^6 & &:= (21-7+67-8+2-33-6)^6 \\ &:= (2-17+6-7+8+23-3-6)^{12} & &:= (-21-7+67-8+2-33+6)^{12} \\ &:= (-2+17+6-7+8+23-3-6)^6 & &:= (-21+7+67+8+2-33+6)^6 \\ &:= (-2-17+6+7-8+23+3-6)^{12} & &:= (21+7-67+8-2+33+6)^{12} \\ &:= (2+17+6-7+8-23-3+6)^{12} & &:= (-21-7+67+8-2-3-36)^{12} \\ &:= (2+17+6-7-8+23-3+6)^6 & &:= (21-7+67-8+2-3-36)^6 \\ &:= (2-17-6-7+8+23-3+6)^{12} & &:= (21+7-67+8-2+3+36)^{12} \\ &:= (-2+17-6-7+8+23-3+6)^6 & &:= (-21-7+6+78-23-3+6)^6 \\ &:= (-2+17+6+7-8-23+3+6)^{12} & &:= (-21+7-6+7+82+3-36)^6 \\ &:= (-2-17-6+7-8+23+3+6)^{12} & &:= (-21+7+6-7-8+233+6)^4 \\ &:= (-2+1-76+7+82+3-3-6)^{12} & &:= (-21-7+6+7-8+233+6)^4 \\ &:= (-2+1-76+7+82-3+3-6)^{12} & &:= (21+7+6-7-8+23-36)^{12} \\ &:= (-2+1+76+7-82+3-3+6)^{12} & &:= (21-7+6+7-8+23-36)^{12} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 &:= (21+7+6+7+8+23-36)^6 & &:= (2-1+76-78-2+3+36)^6 \\
 &:= (21-7-6-7-8-23+36)^{12} & &:= (-2-1-76+78-2+3+36)^6 \\
 &:= (21+7-6-7+8-23+36)^6 & &:= (-2-1+76-78+2+3+36)^6 \\
 &:= (-21+7+6-7+8-23+36)^{12} & &:= (2-1-7+67-82+33-6)^{12} \\
 &:= (21-7-6+7+8-23+36)^6 & &:= (2-1-7-67+82+33-6)^6 \\
 &:= (-21-7+6+7+8-23+36)^{12} & &:= (-2+1+7+67-8-23-36)^{12} \\
 &:= (-21+7+6-7-8+23+36)^6 & &:= (-2-1-7+67+8-23-36)^{12} \\
 &:= (-21-7+6+7-8+23+36)^6 & &:= (-2-1-7+67-8+23-36)^6 \\
 &:= (2+176-7+8-2+33+6)^4 & &:= (-2+1+7-67+8+23+36)^{12} \\
 &:= (-2+176-7+8+2+33+6)^4 & &:= (-21-76+78-2+33-6)^{12} \\
 &:= (2+176-7+8-2+3+36)^4 & &:= (-21+76-78+2+33-6)^{12} \\
 &:= (-2+176-7+8+2+3+36)^4 & &:= (21+76+78+2+33+6)^4 \\
 &:= (-2+17+67-82+3-3+6)^{12} & &:= (21+76+78+2+3+36)^4 \\
 &:= (2-17-67+82+3-3+6)^{12} & &:= (21+7+67+82+33+6)^4 \\
 &:= (-2+17-67+82+3-3+6)^6 & &:= (21+7+67+82+3+36)^4 \\
 &:= (-2+17+67-82-3+3+6)^{12} & &:= (-2+176-7+82+3-36)^4 \\
 &:= (2-17-67+82-3+3+6)^{12} & &:= (-2-17+6+78-23-36)^{12} \\
 &:= (-2+17-67+82-3+3+6)^6 & &:= (2+17+6-78+23+36)^{12} \\
 &:= (-2-17+67+8-23-3+6)^6 & &:= (2+1+76+78+23+36)^4 \\
 &:= (-2-17+6+78-2-33+6)^6 & &:= (-217+6-7-82+336)^6 \\
 &:= (2-1+76-78-2+33+6)^6 & &:= (-21+76-78+233+6)^4 \\
 &:= (-2-1-76+78-2+33+6)^6 & &:= (21+76-78+23-36)^{12} \\
 &:= (-2-1+76-78+2+33+6)^6 & &:= (21-76+78-23+36)^6 \\
 &:= (2+1-76+78-2-3+36)^6 & &:= (-21+76-78+23+36)^6 \\
 &:= (2+1+76-78+2-3+36)^6 & &:= (2+176+782+336)^3 \\
 &:= (-2+1-76+78+2-3+36)^6 & &
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 \mathbf{2186875592} &:= (-2+1868-7-559-2)^3 & &:= (221+7-3+7-3+9-21)^4 \\
 \mathbf{2191933899} &:= (2+1+919-3+389-9)^3 & &:= (22+173+7+3+9+2+1)^4 \\
 &:= (-2-1+919+3+389-9)^3 & &:= (2+2+173+7+3+9+21)^4 \\
 &:= (-21+919+3+389+9)^3 & &:= (221-7-37+39+2-1)^4 \\
 \mathbf{2197546884} &:= (-2-1+9-7-5+46884)^2 & &:= (22+173+7+3-9+21)^4 \\
 &:= (2-1-9+7-5+46884)^2 & &:= (2+2-173-7+392+1)^4 \\
 \mathbf{2217373921} &:= (221+7-3+7-3-9-2-1)^4 & & \mathbf{2219006624} := (2+2+1+9+0066-2-4)^5 \\
 &:= (221-7+3-7-3+9+2-1)^4 & &:= (2-2+1+9+0066+2-4)^5 \\
 &:= (221-7-3-7+3+9+2-1)^4 & &:= (-2+2+1+9+0066+2-4)^5 \\
 &:= (221+7+3-7+3-9-2+1)^4 & &:= (-2-2+1+9+0066-2+4)^5 \\
 &:= (221-7+3+7+3-9-2+1)^4 & &:= (2-2+1+9+006+62-4)^5
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 & := (-2 + 2 + 1 + 9 + 006 + 62 - 4)^5 & := (2 - 3 + 48468 - 5 - 2 + 1)^2 \\
 & := (2 + 2 + 1 + 9 - 006 + 62 + 4)^5 & := (-2 - 3 + 48468 - 5 + 2 + 1)^2 \\
 & := (22 + 1 - 9 + 0066 - 2 - 4)^5 & := (-23 + 48468 - 5 + 21)^2 \\
 & := (22 + 1 - 9 - 006 + 62 + 4)^5 & \mathbf{2348759296} := (-2 + 3 + 48759 - 296)^2 \\
 & := (2 + 21 - 9 + 0066 - 2 - 4)^5 & \mathbf{2355452089} := (-2 - 3554 + 52089)^2 \\
 & := (-2 + 21 - 9 + 0066 + 2 - 4)^5 & \mathbf{2357947691} := (2 + 3 - 5 + 7 + 9 + 4 + 7 - 6 - 9 - 1)^9 \\
 & := (-2 + 21 - 9 + 006 + 62 - 4)^5 & := (-2 - 3 + 5 + 7 + 9 + 4 + 7 - 6 - 9 - 1)^9 \\
 & := (2 + 21 - 9 - 006 + 62 + 4)^5 & := (2 + 3 + 5 + 7 + 9 - 4 - 7 + 6 - 9 - 1)^9 \\
 & := (22 + 1 + 9 + 0066 - 24)^5 & := (2 + 3 + 5 - 7 + 9 - 4 + 7 + 6 - 9 - 1)^9 \\
 & := (2 + 21 + 9 + 0066 - 24)^5 & := (-2 + 3 - 5 + 7 + 9 - 4 + 7 + 6 - 9 - 1)^9 \\
 \mathbf{2224725889} & := (2 - 2 - 2 + 47258 - 89)^2 & := (-2 + 3 + 5 + 7 - 9 + 4 + 7 + 6 - 9 - 1)^9 \\
 & := (-2 + 2 - 2 + 47258 - 89)^2 & := (2 - 3 + 5 + 7 + 9 - 4 - 7 - 6 + 9 - 1)^9 \\
 & := (-2 - 2 + 2 + 47258 - 89)^2 & := (2 + 3 + 5 - 7 + 9 + 4 - 7 - 6 + 9 - 1)^9 \\
 \mathbf{2242496025} & := (-2242 + 49602 - 5)^2 & := (-2 + 3 - 5 + 7 + 9 + 4 - 7 - 6 + 9 - 1)^9 \\
 \mathbf{2242946629} & := (2242 - 946 + 6 - 2 + 9)^3 & := (2 - 3 + 5 - 7 + 9 - 4 + 7 - 6 + 9 - 1)^9 \\
 \mathbf{2258530576} & := (2 + 2 - 5 - 85 + 305 - 7 + 6)^4 & := (-2 - 3 - 5 + 7 + 9 - 4 + 7 - 6 + 9 - 1)^9 \\
 & := (225 - 85 - 3 + 05 + 76)^4 & := (2 + 3 - 5 + 7 - 9 + 4 + 7 - 6 + 9 - 1)^9 \\
 & := (-2 + 258 - 5 + 30 - 57 - 6)^4 & := (-2 - 3 + 5 + 7 - 9 + 4 + 7 - 6 + 9 - 1)^9 \\
 \mathbf{2263475776} & := (-2 - 2 + 6 + 3 + 47577 - 6)^2 & := (-2 + 3 - 5 - 7 + 9 + 4 + 7 - 6 + 9 - 1)^9 \\
 & := (-2 - 2 - 6 + 3 + 47577 + 6)^2 & := (2 + 3 + 5 + 7 - 9 - 4 - 7 + 6 + 9 - 1)^9 \\
 \mathbf{2263571297} & := (22 - 63 + 57 + 1297)^3 & := (-2 + 3 + 5 - 7 + 9 - 4 - 7 + 6 + 9 - 1)^9 \\
 \mathbf{2300257521} & := (2 + 300 - 2 - 5 - 75 - 2 + 1)^4 & := (2 + 3 + 5 - 7 - 9 - 4 + 7 + 6 + 9 - 1)^9 \\
 & := (-2 + 300 + 2 - 5 - 75 - 2 + 1)^4 & := (-2 + 3 - 5 + 7 - 9 - 4 + 7 + 6 + 9 - 1)^9 \\
 & := (-2 + 300 - 2 - 5 - 75 + 2 + 1)^4 & := (-2 + 3 + 5 + 7 + 9 - 4 + 7 - 6 - 9 + 1)^9 \\
 & := (-2 - 30 + 0257 - 5 - 2 + 1)^4 & := (2 + 3 - 5 + 7 + 9 + 4 - 7 + 6 - 9 + 1)^9 \\
 & := (2 + 300 - 25 - 7 - 52 + 1)^4 & := (-2 - 3 + 5 + 7 + 9 + 4 - 7 + 6 - 9 + 1)^9 \\
 & := (2 - 300 - 2 + 5 - 7 + 521)^4 & := (2 - 3 - 5 + 7 + 9 - 4 + 7 + 6 - 9 + 1)^9 \\
 & := (-2 - 300 + 2 + 5 - 7 + 521)^4 & := (2 - 3 + 5 + 7 - 9 + 4 + 7 + 6 - 9 + 1)^9 \\
 & := (-2 - 300 - 2 - 5 + 7 + 521)^4 & := (2 + 3 - 5 - 7 + 9 + 4 + 7 + 6 - 9 + 1)^9 \\
 & := (-2 + 300 - 25 - 75 + 21)^4 & := (-2 - 3 + 5 - 7 + 9 + 4 + 7 + 6 - 9 + 1)^9 \\
 \mathbf{2310148096} & := (-2 - 31 + 01 + 48096)^2 & := (2 - 3 - 5 + 7 + 9 + 4 - 7 - 6 + 9 + 1)^9 \\
 & := (-23 - 10 + 1 + 48096)^2 & := (-2 + 3 + 5 + 7 - 9 - 4 + 7 - 6 + 9 + 1)^9 \\
 \mathbf{2310438248} & := (23 + 1043 + 8 + 248)^3 & := (2 - 3 - 5 - 7 + 9 + 4 + 7 - 6 + 9 + 1)^9 \\
 \mathbf{2312648100} & := (2 - 3 - 1 - 2 - 6 + 48100)^2 & := (2 - 3 + 5 - 7 + 9 - 4 - 7 + 6 + 9 + 1)^9 \\
 & := (-2 - 3 - 1 + 2 - 6 + 48100)^2 & := (-2 - 3 - 5 + 7 + 9 - 4 - 7 + 6 + 9 + 1)^9 \\
 \mathbf{2342560000} & := (-2 - 34 + 256 + 0000)^4 & := (2 + 3 - 5 + 7 - 9 + 4 - 7 + 6 + 9 + 1)^9 \\
 & := (2 - 342 + 560 + 000)^4 & := (-2 - 3 + 5 + 7 - 9 + 4 - 7 + 6 + 9 + 1)^9 \\
 \mathbf{2348468521} & := (-2 + 3 + 48468 - 5 - 2 - 1)^2 & := (-2 + 3 - 5 - 7 + 9 + 4 - 7 + 6 + 9 + 1)^9
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} &:= (2-3-5+7-9-4+7+6+9+1)^9 &:= (-2+3-5+7+94-76-9-1)^9 \\ &:= (-2-3-5-7+9-4+7+6+9+1)^9 &:= (2-3-5+7+94-76-9+1)^9 \\ &:= (2+3-5-7-9+4+7+6+9+1)^9 &:= (-2-3-5-7+94-76+9+1)^9 \\ &:= (-2-3+5-7-9+4+7+6+9+1)^9 &:= (2+3-5+7+94+7-6-91)^9 \\ &:= (23+5-7+9+4-7-6-9-1)^9 &:= (-2-3+5+7+94+7-6-91)^9 \\ &:= (23-5+7-9+4+7-6-9-1)^9 &:= (-2+3+5+7-94+7-6+91)^9 \\ &:= (23+5+7-9-4-7+6-9-1)^9 &:= (2-3-5+7-94+7+6+91)^9 \\ &:= (23+5-7-9-4+7+6-9-1)^9 &:= (-2+3+5-7-9-47+69-1)^9 \\ &:= (23-5-7+9-4-7-6+9-1)^9 &:= (2-3+5-7-9-47+69+1)^9 \\ &:= (23+5-7-9+4-7-6+9-1)^9 &:= (-2-3-5+7-9-47+69+1)^9 \\ &:= (-23+5+7+9+4+7-6+9-1)^9 &:= (-2+3+5+7+9+4+76-91)^9 \\ &:= (23-5+7-9+4-7+6-9+1)^9 &:= (2-3-5+7-9+4-76+91)^9 \\ &:= (23-5-7-9+4+7+6-9+1)^9 &:= (-2-3-5-7+9+4-76+91)^9 \\ &:= (-23+5+7+9+4-7+6+9+1)^9 &:= (-23-57+94-7-6+9+1)^9 \\ &:= (-23+5-7+9+4+7+6+9+1)^9 &:= (-23-57+9-4+76+9+1)^9 \\ &:= (-2+3-5-7-9+47-6-9-1)^9 &:= (-23-57+9+4-7-6+91)^9 \\ &:= (2-3-5-7-9+47-6-9+1)^9 &:= (-23-57-9-4+7+6+91)^9 \\ &:= (-23+5+7-9+47-6-9-1)^9 &:= (23+5-79-4+76-9-1)^9 \\ &:= (23+5+7+9-47+6+9-1)^9 &:= (23-5-79+4+76-9+1)^9 \\ &:= (-23+5-7-9+47+6-9+1)^9 &:= (23-5+79+4+7-6-91)^9 \\ &:= (-2-35-7-9-4+76-9+1)^9 &:= (23+5+79-4-7+6-91)^9 \\ &:= (-2-3-57+94-7-6-9+1)^9 &:= (-23+5-79+4+7+6+91)^9 \\ &:= (-2-3-57+9-4+76-9+1)^9 &:= (23+5-7-94+76+9-1)^9 \\ &:= (2+3-57-9+4+76-9+1)^9 &:= (23+5-7+94-7-6-91)^9 \\ &:= (-2-3-57-9-4+76+9+1)^9 &:= (23-5+7+9+47-69-1)^9 \\ &:= (-2-3-57-9+4-7-6+91)^9 &:= (-23-5+7+9-47+69+1)^9 \\ &:= (2-3+5+79-4-76+9-1)^9 &:= (23+5-7+9-4+76-91)^9 \\ &:= (-2+3-5+79+4-76+9-1)^9 &:= (-2-35+79-47+6+9+1)^9 \\ &:= (2+3+5-79-4+76+9-1)^9 &:= (-2+35-79-4-7+69-1)^9 \\ &:= (2-3-5+79+4-76+9+1)^9 &:= (2+35+7-94-7+69-1)^9 \\ &:= (2+3-5-79+4+76+9+1)^9 &:= (2+35-7-94+7+69-1)^9 \\ &:= (-2-3+5-79+4+76+9+1)^9 &:= (-2+35+7+9+47+6-91)^9 \\ &:= (-2+3+5+79+4+7+6-91)^9 &:= (-2-35+7-9-47+6+91)^9 \\ &:= (2-3-5-79+4+7-6+91)^9 &:= (-2-3+57+9+47-6-91)^9 \\ &:= (2-3+5-79-4-7+6+91)^9 &:= (-2+3+57-9+47+6-91)^9 \\ &:= (-2+3-5-79+4-7+6+91)^9 &:= (-23+5+79+47-6-91)^9 \\ &:= (-2-3-5-79-4+7+6+91)^9 &:= (-2-3-57-94+76+91)^9 \\ &:= (2+3+5-7+94-76-9-1)^9 &:= (2+35-794+769-1)^9 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 &:= (2 - 3 + 579 - 476 - 91)^9 \\
 &:= (23 - 579 + 476 + 91)^9 \\
 \mathbf{2363266368} &:= (23 + 632 + 663 + 6 + 8)^3 \\
 \mathbf{2373046875} &:= (2 + 3 + 7 - 3 + 046 + 8 + 7 + 5)^5 \\
 &:= (2 - 3 + 7 + 3 + 046 + 8 + 7 + 5)^5 \\
 &:= (2 + 3 + 7 + 3 + 04 + 68 - 7 - 5)^5 \\
 &:= (2 + 3 + 7 - 3 - 04 + 68 + 7 - 5)^5 \\
 &:= (2 - 3 + 7 + 3 - 04 + 68 + 7 - 5)^5 \\
 &:= (2 + 3 - 7 + 3 + 04 + 68 + 7 - 5)^5 \\
 &:= (-2 + 3 + 7 - 3 + 04 + 68 - 7 + 5)^5 \\
 &:= (-2 - 3 + 7 + 3 + 04 + 68 - 7 + 5)^5 \\
 &:= (-2 - 3 + 7 - 3 - 04 + 68 + 7 + 5)^5 \\
 &:= (-2 + 3 - 7 - 3 + 04 + 68 + 7 + 5)^5 \\
 &:= (-2 - 3 - 7 + 3 + 04 + 68 + 7 + 5)^5 \\
 &:= (2 - 3 + 7 - 3 - 04 - 6 + 87 - 5)^5 \\
 &:= (2 + 3 - 7 - 3 + 04 - 6 + 87 - 5)^5 \\
 &:= (2 - 3 - 7 + 3 + 04 - 6 + 87 - 5)^5 \\
 &:= (-2 + 3 - 7 - 3 - 04 + 6 + 87 - 5)^5 \\
 &:= (-2 - 3 - 7 + 3 - 04 + 6 + 87 - 5)^5 \\
 &:= (-2 - 3 - 7 - 3 + 04 - 6 + 87 + 5)^5 \\
 &:= (23 + 7 + 3 + 046 + 8 - 7 - 5)^5 \\
 &:= (23 - 7 + 3 + 046 + 8 + 7 - 5)^5 \\
 &:= (23 - 7 - 3 - 04 + 68 - 7 + 5)^5 \\
 &:= (-23 + 7 - 3 - 04 + 6 + 87 + 5)^5 \\
 &:= (-23 - 7 + 3 + 04 + 6 + 87 + 5)^5 \\
 &:= (2 + 37 + 30 + 4 + 6 + 8 - 7 - 5)^5 \\
 &:= (2 + 37 + 30 - 4 + 6 - 8 + 7 + 5)^5 \\
 &:= (-2 + 37 + 30 - 4 - 6 + 8 + 7 + 5)^5 \\
 &:= (-2 - 3 - 7 + 30 - 4 - 6 - 8 + 75)^5 \\
 &:= (2 + 3 + 7 - 30 + 4 + 6 + 8 + 75)^5 \\
 &:= (2 + 37 - 30 + 46 + 8 + 7 + 5)^5 \\
 &:= (2 + 37 - 30 - 4 + 68 + 7 - 5)^5 \\
 &:= (-2 + 37 - 30 + 4 + 68 - 7 + 5)^5 \\
 &:= (-2 - 37 + 30 + 4 + 68 + 7 + 5)^5 \\
 &:= (2 - 37 + 30 + 4 - 6 + 87 - 5)^5 \\
 &:= (-2 - 37 + 30 - 4 + 6 + 87 - 5)^5 \\
 &:= (2 - 37 - 3 + 046 - 8 + 75)^5 \\
 &:= (-2 + 37 + 3 - 046 + 8 + 75)^5 \\
 &:= (2 + 3 + 73 + 04 + 68 - 75)^5 \\
 &:= (2 - 3 + 73 - 04 - 68 + 75)^5 \\
 &:= (-2 + 3 - 73 + 04 + 68 + 75)^5 \\
 &:= (2 - 3 - 7 - 30 + 46 - 8 + 75)^5 \\
 &:= (-2 + 3 + 7 + 30 - 46 + 8 + 75)^5 \\
 &:= (23 + 73 + 046 + 8 - 75)^5 \\
 &:= (23 + 730 + 4 - 687 + 5)^5 \\
 \mathbf{2380464100} &:= (2380 + 46410 + 0)^2 \\
 \mathbf{2384621056} &:= (2384 + 6 + 2 - 1056)^3 \\
 \mathbf{2384857225} &:= (238 + 48572 + 25)^2 \\
 \mathbf{2385443281} &:= (238 + 5 - 4 - 4 - 3 - 2 - 8 - 1)^4 \\
 &:= (238 - 5 - 4 - 4 + 3 + 2 - 8 - 1)^4 \\
 &:= (238 - 5 + 4 - 4 - 3 - 2 - 8 + 1)^4 \\
 &:= (238 - 5 - 4 + 4 - 3 - 2 - 8 + 1)^4 \\
 &:= (238 + 5 + 4 + 4 - 3 - 28 + 1)^4 \\
 &:= (-2 + 3 - 8 - 54 + 4 - 3 + 281)^4 \\
 &:= (-2 - 3 - 8 - 54 + 4 + 3 + 281)^4 \\
 &:= (238 - 54 - 4 + 32 + 8 + 1)^4 \\
 &:= (-238 + 5 + 443 + 2 + 8 + 1)^4 \\
 &:= (238 - 5 - 44 + 3 + 28 + 1)^4 \\
 &:= (238 - 5 + 4 - 43 + 28 - 1)^4 \\
 &:= (-23 - 85 + 4 - 4 + 328 + 1)^4 \\
 &:= (-23 - 85 - 4 + 4 + 328 + 1)^4 \\
 &:= (23 + 85 + 4 - 4 + 32 + 81)^4 \\
 &:= (23 + 85 - 4 + 4 + 32 + 81)^4 \\
 &:= (23 - 85 - 44 + 328 - 1)^4 \\
 &:= (-238 - 54 + 432 + 81)^4 \\
 &:= (-2 + 385 - 443 + 281)^4 \\
 \mathbf{2411494821} &:= (24 + 1 + 1 + 494 + 821)^3 \\
 \mathbf{2416893688} &:= (-2 + 416 + 8 + 936 - 8 - 8)^3 \\
 &:= (-2 + 416 - 8 + 936 + 8 - 8)^3 \\
 &:= (-2 + 416 - 8 + 936 - 8 + 8)^3 \\
 \mathbf{2417492224} &:= (-2 - 41 - 7 + 49222 - 4)^2 \\
 \mathbf{2426449081} &:= (242 - 64 + 49081)^2 \\
 \mathbf{2428912656} &:= (242 + 8 - 9 - 12 - 6 + 5 - 6)^4 \\
 &:= (2 - 4 + 289 - 1 - 2 - 6 - 56)^4 \\
 &:= (-2 - 4 + 289 - 1 + 2 - 6 - 56)^4 \\
 &:= (2 + 4 + 2 + 89 + 126 + 5 - 6)^4
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 & := (2 - 4 - 2 + 89 + 126 + 5 + 6)^4 & := (2 + 4 + 9 + 4 - 3 + 5 - 7 + 8 + 8 - 8)^7 \\
 & := (-2 - 4 + 2 + 89 + 126 + 5 + 6)^4 & := (-2 + 4 + 9 + 4 - 3 - 5 + 7 + 8 + 8 - 8)^7 \\
 & := (2 - 428 - 9 - 1 + 2 + 656)^4 & := (-2 - 4 + 9 - 4 + 3 + 5 + 7 + 8 + 8 - 8)^7 \\
 & := (-24 - 2 - 8 + 912 - 656)^4 & := (-2 + 4 + 9 + 4 + 3 + 5 + 7 - 8 - 8 + 8)^7 \\
 & := (-2 - 4 - 28 + 912 - 656)^4 & := (2 + 4 + 9 + 4 - 3 + 5 - 7 + 8 - 8 + 8)^7 \\
 \mathbf{2433138625} & := (2 - 43 + 3 + 1386 + 2 - 5)^3 & := (-2 + 4 + 9 + 4 - 3 - 5 + 7 + 8 - 8 + 8)^7 \\
 & := (2 - 43 - 3 + 1386 - 2 + 5)^3 & := (-2 - 4 + 9 - 4 + 3 + 5 + 7 + 8 - 8 + 8)^7 \\
 & := (-2 - 43 - 3 + 1386 + 2 + 5)^3 & := (2 + 4 + 9 + 4 - 3 + 5 - 7 - 8 + 8 + 8)^7 \\
 \mathbf{2438569736} & := (-24 + 385 + 6 + 973 + 6)^3 & := (-2 + 4 + 9 + 4 - 3 - 5 + 7 - 8 + 8 + 8)^7 \\
 \mathbf{2444008923} & := (-24 + 440 + 08 + 923)^3 & := (-2 - 4 + 9 - 4 + 3 + 5 + 7 - 8 + 8 + 8)^7 \\
 \mathbf{2449458064} & := (24 + 49458 + 06 + 4)^2 & := (-2 + 4 + 9 - 4 + 3 - 5 - 7 + 8 + 8 + 8)^7 \\
 \mathbf{2450250000} & := (-2 + 4 - 502 + 50000)^2 & := (-2 - 4 + 9 + 4 + 3 - 5 - 7 + 8 + 8 + 8)^7 \\
 \mathbf{2454911549} & := (2 + 454 + 911 - 5 - 4 - 9)^3 & := (2 - 4 + 9 - 4 - 3 + 5 - 7 + 8 + 8 + 8)^7 \\
 \mathbf{2456490969} & := (2 + 456 + 49096 + 9)^2 & := (-2 + 4 - 9 + 4 + 3 + 5 - 7 + 8 + 8 + 8)^7 \\
 \mathbf{2472973441} & := (247 - 2 - 9 - 7 + 3 - 4 - 4 - 1)^4 & := (-2 - 4 + 9 - 4 - 3 - 5 + 7 + 8 + 8 + 8)^7 \\
 & := (247 + 2 - 9 - 7 - 3 - 4 - 4 + 1)^4 & := (2 + 4 - 9 - 4 + 3 - 5 + 7 + 8 + 8 + 8)^7 \\
 & := (247 - 29 + 7 - 3 + 4 - 4 + 1)^4 & := (2 - 4 - 9 + 4 + 3 - 5 + 7 + 8 + 8 + 8)^7 \\
 & := (247 - 29 + 7 - 3 - 4 + 4 + 1)^4 & := (-2 + 4 - 9 - 4 - 3 + 5 + 7 + 8 + 8 + 8)^7 \\
 & := (247 - 29 - 7 + 3 + 4 + 4 + 1)^4 & := (-2 - 4 - 9 + 4 - 3 + 5 + 7 + 8 + 8 + 8)^7 \\
 & := (247 + 2 + 9 + 7 + 3 - 44 - 1)^4 & := (24 + 9 + 4 - 3 + 5 + 7 - 8 - 8 - 8)^7 \\
 & := (247 + 2 + 9 + 7 + 3 - 4 - 41)^4 & := (24 + 9 - 4 + 3 + 5 - 7 + 8 - 8 - 8)^7 \\
 & := (2 + 4 + 72 + 97 + 3 + 44 + 1)^4 & := (24 + 9 - 4 + 3 + 5 - 7 - 8 + 8 - 8)^7 \\
 & := (2 + 4 + 72 + 97 + 3 + 4 + 41)^4 & := (24 + 9 - 4 - 3 - 5 - 7 + 8 + 8 - 8)^7 \\
 & := (247 + 29 - 7 - 3 - 44 + 1)^4 & := (24 - 9 + 4 - 3 + 5 - 7 + 8 + 8 - 8)^7 \\
 & := (24 + 72 + 9 + 73 + 44 + 1)^4 & := (24 + 9 - 4 + 3 + 5 - 7 - 8 - 8 + 8)^7 \\
 & := (24 + 72 + 9 + 73 + 4 + 41)^4 & := (24 + 9 - 4 - 3 - 5 - 7 + 8 - 8 + 8)^7 \\
 & := (2 - 47 + 297 - 34 + 4 + 1)^4 & := (24 - 9 + 4 - 3 + 5 - 7 + 8 - 8 + 8)^7 \\
 & := (2 + 47 + 2 + 97 + 34 + 41)^4 & := (24 + 9 - 4 - 3 - 5 - 7 - 8 + 8 + 8)^7 \\
 & := (-2 - 4 + 7 + 297 - 34 - 41)^4 & := (24 - 9 + 4 - 3 + 5 - 7 - 8 + 8 + 8)^7 \\
 & := (247 - 2 - 97 + 34 + 41)^4 & := (-24 + 9 + 4 - 3 + 5 + 7 + 8 + 8 + 8)^7 \\
 \mathbf{2476813977} & := (-2 - 47 + 6 - 8 + 1397 + 7)^3 & := (2 + 49 + 4 + 3 - 5 - 7 - 8 - 8 - 8)^7 \\
 & := (24 + 7 - 68 + 1397 - 7)^3 & := (-2 + 49 + 4 - 3 + 5 - 7 - 8 - 8 - 8)^7 \\
 & := (24 - 7 - 68 + 1397 + 7)^3 & := (2 + 49 - 4 - 3 - 5 + 7 - 8 - 8 - 8)^7 \\
 \mathbf{2482309864} & := (2 + 482 - 3 + 09 + 864)^3 & := (2 + 4 + 9 + 43 - 5 - 7 - 8 - 8 - 8)^7 \\
 \mathbf{2487813875} & := (-2 + 487 + 8 - 13 + 875)^3 & := (2 - 4 - 9 + 43 + 5 - 7 + 8 - 8 - 8)^7 \\
 \mathbf{2490608836} & := (2 + 49060 + 8 + 836)^2 & := (-2 - 4 - 9 + 43 - 5 + 7 + 8 - 8 - 8)^7 \\
 \mathbf{2494357888} & := (-2 + 4 + 9 + 4 + 3 + 5 + 7 + 8 - 8 - 8)^7 & := (2 - 4 - 9 + 43 + 5 - 7 - 8 + 8 - 8)^7 \\
 & := (-2 + 4 + 9 + 4 + 3 + 5 + 7 - 8 + 8 - 8)^7 & := (-2 - 4 - 9 + 43 - 5 + 7 - 8 + 8 - 8)^7
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 &:= (2-4-9+43+5-7-8-8+8)^7 \\
 &:= (-2-4-9+43-5+7-8-8+8)^7 \\
 &:= (24-9+43-5-7-8-8-8)^7 \\
 &:= (-24+9+43-5+7+8-8-8)^7 \\
 &:= (-24+9+43-5+7-8+8-8)^7 \\
 &:= (-24+9+43-5+7-8-8+8)^7 \\
 &:= (-24-9+43-5-7+8+8+8)^7 \\
 &:= (2-49+43-5+7+8+8+8)^7 \\
 &:= (2-49+4-3-5-7+88-8)^7 \\
 &:= (2-49+4-3-5-7-8+88)^7 \\
 &:= (-2-4+94-35-7-8-8-8)^7 \\
 &:= (2+4+94+3-57-8-8-8)^7 \\
 &:= (2-4+94+3+5-78+8-8)^7 \\
 &:= (2-4+94+3+5-78-8+8)^7 \\
 &:= (2-4+94-3-5-78+8+8)^7 \\
 &:= (2+4-9-43-5-7+88-8)^7 \\
 &:= (2+4-9-43-5-7-8+88)^7 \\
 &:= (24+94+3-5-78-8-8)^7 \\
 &:= (24-94+3-5+78+8+8)^7 \\
 &:= (-24-9-43-5+7+88+8)^7 \\
 &:= (-24-9-43-5+7+8+88)^7 \\
 &:= (-24-9-4-35+78+8+8)^7 \\
 &:= (-2+49+43+5+7-88+8)^7 \\
 &:= (-2+49+43+5+7+8-88)^7 \\
 &:= (-2-4-94+35+7+88-8)^7 \\
 &:= (-2-4-94+35+7-8+88)^7 \\
 &:= (-2+4-9+4+35+78-88)^7 \\
 &:= (-24-94+3+57+88-8)^7 \\
 &:= (-24-94+3+57-8+88)^7 \\
 &:= (2+49-4-35-78+88)^7 \\
 &:= (24+943-57-888)^7 \\
 \mathbf{2499500025} &:= (2-4+9-9+50002-5)^2 \\
 &:= (2-4-9+9+50002-5)^2 \\
 &:= (2+4-9-9+50002+5)^2 \\
 \mathbf{2501500225} &:= (2-5+01+50022-5)^2 \\
 \mathbf{2505002500} &:= (25+050025+00)^2 \\
 \mathbf{2509408836} &:= (-2+50940-8-836)^2 \\
 \mathbf{2509911279} &:= (250+991+127-9)^3 \\
 \mathbf{2517630976} &:= (251+7+6-30-9-7+6)^4 \\
 &:= (251-7+6-30-9+7+6)^4 \\
 &:= (-2+5+1-76+309-7-6)^4 \\
 &:= (-2-5-1-76+309-7+6)^4 \\
 &:= (-2+5+1-7-6+309-76)^4 \\
 &:= (-2-5-1-7+6+309-76)^4 \\
 &:= (-2-5+176-30+9+76)^4 \\
 &:= (-25+176-30+97+6)^4 \\
 \mathbf{2522450176} &:= (2+52-2-4+50176)^2 \\
 &:= (-2+52+2-4+50176)^2 \\
 \mathbf{2532139147} &:= (2+5-32+1391+4-7)^3 \\
 &:= (-2-5-32+1391+4+7)^3 \\
 \mathbf{2535525376} &:= (2+53+5+5+2+5+3+7-6)^5 \\
 &:= (2+5+3+55+2+5+3+7-6)^5 \\
 &:= (2+5-3+55+2+5-3+7+6)^5 \\
 &:= (2+5+3+5+52+5+3+7-6)^5 \\
 &:= (2+5-3+5+52+5-3+7+6)^5 \\
 &:= (2+5+3+5+5+2+53+7-6)^5 \\
 &:= (2+5+3+5-5-2-5-3+76)^5 \\
 &:= (2+5+3-5+5-2-5-3+76)^5 \\
 &:= (-2+5-3+5+5-2-5-3+76)^5 \\
 &:= (2-5+3+5+5-2-5-3+76)^5 \\
 &:= (-2+5+3+5-5+2-5-3+76)^5 \\
 &:= (-2+5+3-5+5+2-5-3+76)^5 \\
 &:= (-2-5+3+5+5+2-5-3+76)^5 \\
 &:= (2+5+3-5-5-2+5-3+76)^5 \\
 &:= (-2+5-3+5-5-2+5-3+76)^5 \\
 &:= (2-5+3+5-5-2+5-3+76)^5 \\
 &:= (-2+5-3-5+5-2+5-3+76)^5 \\
 &:= (2-5+3-5+5-2+5-3+76)^5 \\
 &:= (-2-5-3+5+5-2+5-3+76)^5 \\
 &:= (-2+5+3-5-5+2+5-3+76)^5 \\
 &:= (-2-5+3+5-5+2+5-3+76)^5 \\
 &:= (-2-5+3-5+5+2+5-3+76)^5 \\
 &:= (2+5-3+5-5-2-5+3+76)^5 \\
 &:= (2+5-3-5+5-2-5+3+76)^5 \\
 &:= (2-5-3+5+5-2-5+3+76)^5 \\
 &:= (2+5+3-5-5+2-5+3+76)^5
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} & := (-2+5-3+5-5+2-5+3+76)^5 & := (25+3-5+5-25-3+76)^5 \\ & := (2-5+3+5-5+2-5+3+76)^5 & := (-25+3+5-5+25-3+76)^5 \\ & := (-2+5-3-5+5+2-5+3+76)^5 & := (-25+3-5+5+25-3+76)^5 \\ & := (2-5+3-5+5+2-5+3+76)^5 & := (25-3+5-5-25+3+76)^5 \\ & := (-2-5-3+5+5+2-5+3+76)^5 & := (25-3-5+5-25+3+76)^5 \\ & := (2+5-3-5-5-2+5+3+76)^5 & := (-25-3+5-5+25+3+76)^5 \\ & := (2-5-3+5-5-2+5+3+76)^5 & := (-25-3-5+5+25+3+76)^5 \\ & := (2-5-3-5+5-2+5+3+76)^5 & := (2+53+55+2-5-37+6)^5 \\ & := (-2+5-3-5-5+2+5+3+76)^5 & := (2+53-55-2+5-3+76)^5 \\ & := (2-5+3-5-5+2+5+3+76)^5 & := (-2-53+55-2+5-3+76)^5 \\ & := (-2-5-3+5-5+2+5+3+76)^5 & := (-2+53-55+2+5-3+76)^5 \\ & := (-2-5-3-5+5+2+5+3+76)^5 & := (2-53+55-2-5+3+76)^5 \\ & := (25+35+5+2+5+3+7-6)^5 & := (2+53-55+2-5+3+76)^5 \\ & := (25+3+55-2+5+3-7-6)^5 & := (-2-53+55+2-5+3+76)^5 \\ & := (25+3+55+2-5-3-7+6)^5 & := (2+53+5+52-5-37+6)^5 \\ & := (25-3+55-2+5-3-7+6)^5 & := (2+53-5+52+5-37+6)^5 \\ & := (25-3+55+2-5+3-7+6)^5 & := (2+53+5-52-5-3+76)^5 \\ & := (25+3+5+52-5-3-7+6)^5 & := (2+53-5-52+5-3+76)^5 \\ & := (25+3-5+52+5-3-7+6)^5 & := (-2-53+5+52-5+3+76)^5 \\ & := (25-3+5+52-5+3-7+6)^5 & := (-2-53-5+52+5+3+76)^5 \\ & := (25-3-5+52+5+3-7+6)^5 & := (2+53+5-5-2-53+76)^5 \\ & := (25+3+5+5-2+53-7-6)^5 & := (2+53-5+5-2-53+76)^5 \\ & := (25-3+5-5+2+53-7+6)^5 & := (-2+53+5-5+2-53+76)^5 \\ & := (25-3-5+5+2+53-7+6)^5 & := (-2+53-5+5+2-53+76)^5 \\ & := (25-3-5-5-2+53+7+6)^5 & := (2-53+5-5-2+53+76)^5 \\ & := (25+3+5+5+2+5+37-6)^5 & := (2-53-5+5-2+53+76)^5 \\ & := (-2+53+5+5+25+3-7-6)^5 & := (-2-53+5-5+2+53+76)^5 \\ & := (2+53+5-5+25-3-7+6)^5 & := (-2-53-5+5+2+53+76)^5 \\ & := (2+53-5+5+25-3-7+6)^5 & := (2+5-35+52+53-7+6)^5 \\ & := (-2+53-5-5+25-3+7+6)^5 & := (-2-5-35+52+53+7+6)^5 \\ & := (2+5+35+5+25+3+7-6)^5 & := (-2+5-3+55-2-53+76)^5 \\ & := (-2+5+3+55+25+3-7-6)^5 & := (2-5+3+55-2-53+76)^5 \\ & := (-2+5-3+55+25-3-7+6)^5 & := (-2-5+3+55+2-53+76)^5 \\ & := (2-5+3+55+25-3-7+6)^5 & := (2+5-3-55-2+53+76)^5 \\ & := (2-5-3+55+25+3-7+6)^5 & := (-2+5-3-55+2+53+76)^5 \\ & := (2+5+3+5+5+25+37-6)^5 & := (2-5+3-55+2+53+76)^5 \\ & := (25+35-5+25-3-7+6)^5 & := (-2+5+3-5+52-53+76)^5 \\ & := (25+3+5-5-25-3+76)^5 & := (-2-5+3+5+52-53+76)^5 \end{aligned}$$

$:= (2 + 5 - 3 - 5 - 52 + 53 + 76)^5$	$:= (-2 - 5 - 6 - 2 + 8 + 9 + 06 + 2 + 5)^8$
$:= (2 - 5 - 3 + 5 - 52 + 53 + 76)^5$	$:= (25 + 6 - 2 + 8 - 9 - 06 - 2 - 5)^8$
$:= (25 + 35 + 52 - 5 - 37 + 6)^5$	$:= (25 + 6 + 2 - 8 - 9 + 06 - 2 - 5)^8$
$:= (25 + 35 - 52 - 5 - 3 + 76)^5$	$:= (25 - 6 - 2 + 8 - 9 + 06 - 2 - 5)^8$
$:= (-25 - 35 + 52 + 5 + 3 + 76)^5$	$:= (25 + 6 - 2 - 8 - 9 + 06 + 2 - 5)^8$
$:= (25 + 35 - 5 - 2 - 53 + 76)^5$	$:= (25 - 6 - 2 - 8 + 9 - 06 - 2 + 5)^8$
$:= (-25 - 35 + 5 + 2 + 53 + 76)^5$	$:= (-2 + 5 + 6 + 28 - 9 - 06 - 2 - 5)^8$
$:= (253 + 5 - 5 - 253 + 76)^5$	$:= (2 - 5 - 6 + 28 + 9 - 06 - 2 - 5)^8$
$:= (253 - 5 + 5 - 253 + 76)^5$	$:= (-2 + 5 - 6 + 28 - 9 + 06 - 2 - 5)^8$
$:= (-253 + 5 - 5 + 253 + 76)^5$	$:= (-2 - 5 - 6 + 28 + 9 - 06 + 2 - 5)^8$
$:= (-253 - 5 + 5 + 253 + 76)^5$	$:= (-2 - 5 + 6 + 28 - 9 - 06 - 2 + 5)^8$
$:= (-25 + 355 - 253 - 7 + 6)^5$	$:= (-2 - 5 - 6 + 28 - 9 + 06 - 2 + 5)^8$
$:= (2 + 53 + 552 - 537 + 6)^5$	$:= (-2 - 5 + 6 - 2 + 8 - 9 - 06 + 25)^8$
2537716544 $:= (2 + 53 + 771 - 6 + 544)^3$	$:= (-2 + 5 - 6 - 2 - 8 + 9 - 06 + 25)^8$
2550351001 $:= (-2 + 5 - 503 + 51001)^2$	$:= (2 - 5 + 6 - 2 - 8 - 9 + 06 + 25)^8$
2554497863 $:= (25 + 544 + 9 + 786 + 3)^3$	$:= (-2 - 5 + 6 + 2 - 8 - 9 + 06 + 25)^8$
2560108032 $:= (2 + 560 + 1 + 0803 + 2)^3$	$:= (-2 - 5 - 6 - 2 + 8 - 9 + 06 + 25)^8$
$:= (256 + 01080 + 32)^3$	$:= (25 + 6 - 28 + 9 + 06 + 2 - 5)^8$
2562890625 $:= (2 + 5 + 6 - 2 + 8 + 9 - 06 - 2 - 5)^8$	$:= (-25 + 6 + 28 + 9 - 06 - 2 + 5)^8$
$:= (-2 + 5 + 6 + 2 + 8 + 9 - 06 - 2 - 5)^8$	$:= (-25 - 6 + 28 + 9 + 06 - 2 + 5)^8$
$:= (2 + 5 + 6 + 2 - 8 + 9 + 06 - 2 - 5)^8$	$:= (25 + 6 - 2 + 8 + 9 - 06 - 25)^8$
$:= (2 + 5 - 6 - 2 + 8 + 9 + 06 - 2 - 5)^8$	$:= (25 + 6 + 2 - 8 + 9 + 06 - 25)^8$
$:= (-2 + 5 - 6 + 2 + 8 + 9 + 06 - 2 - 5)^8$	$:= (25 - 6 - 2 + 8 + 9 + 06 - 25)^8$
$:= (-2 + 5 + 6 - 2 + 8 + 9 - 06 + 2 - 5)^8$	$:= (-25 + 6 - 2 + 8 + 9 - 06 + 25)^8$
$:= (2 + 5 + 6 - 2 - 8 + 9 + 06 + 2 - 5)^8$	$:= (-25 + 6 + 2 - 8 + 9 + 06 + 25)^8$
$:= (-2 + 5 + 6 + 2 - 8 + 9 + 06 + 2 - 5)^8$	$:= (-25 - 6 - 2 + 8 + 9 + 06 + 25)^8$
$:= (-2 + 5 - 6 - 2 + 8 + 9 + 06 + 2 - 5)^8$	$:= (2 - 5 - 62 + 89 - 06 + 2 - 5)^8$
$:= (2 - 5 + 6 - 2 + 8 + 9 - 06 - 2 + 5)^8$	$:= (-2 + 5 + 62 + 8 + 9 - 062 - 5)^8$
$:= (-2 - 5 + 6 + 2 + 8 + 9 - 06 - 2 + 5)^8$	$:= (-2 + 5 - 62 + 8 + 9 + 062 - 5)^8$
$:= (-2 + 5 + 6 - 2 + 8 - 9 + 06 - 2 + 5)^8$	$:= (-2 - 5 + 62 + 8 + 9 - 062 + 5)^8$
$:= (2 - 5 + 6 + 2 - 8 + 9 + 06 - 2 + 5)^8$	$:= (-2 - 5 - 62 + 8 + 9 + 062 + 5)^8$
$:= (2 - 5 - 6 - 2 + 8 + 9 + 06 - 2 + 5)^8$	$:= (-2 + 5 + 6 + 28 + 9 - 06 - 25)^8$
$:= (-2 - 5 - 6 + 2 + 8 + 9 + 06 - 2 + 5)^8$	$:= (-2 + 5 - 6 + 28 + 9 + 06 - 25)^8$
$:= (2 + 5 + 6 + 2 + 8 - 9 - 06 + 2 + 5)^8$	$:= (2 - 5 + 6 - 28 + 9 + 06 + 25)^8$
$:= (-2 - 5 + 6 - 2 + 8 + 9 - 06 + 2 + 5)^8$	$:= (2 - 5 - 6 + 2 + 89 - 062 - 5)^8$
$:= (2 + 5 - 6 + 2 + 8 - 9 + 06 + 2 + 5)^8$	$:= (-25 - 62 + 89 + 06 + 2 + 5)^8$
$:= (2 - 5 + 6 - 2 - 8 + 9 + 06 + 2 + 5)^8$	$:= (-25 + 6 + 2 + 89 - 062 + 5)^8$
$:= (-2 - 5 + 6 + 2 - 8 + 9 + 06 + 2 + 5)^8$	$:= (2 + 56 - 2 - 8 - 90 + 62 - 5)^8$

$$\begin{aligned}
 & := (-2 + 56 + 2 - 8 - 90 + 62 - 5)^8 \\
 & := (2 + 56 + 2 + 8 + 90 + 62 + 5)^4 \\
 & := (2 - 56 + 2 + 8 + 90 - 6 - 25)^8 \\
 & := (2 + 5 + 62 + 89 + 062 + 5)^4 \\
 & := (2 + 5 - 62 + 89 + 06 - 25)^8 \\
 & := (2 - 5 + 6 + 289 - 062 - 5)^4 \\
 & := (-25 + 62 - 89 + 062 + 5)^8 \\
 & := (2 + 56 + 28 - 90 - 6 + 25)^8 \\
 & := (-2 + 5 + 628 + 9 - 0625)^8 \\
 & := (256 + 28 - 90 + 6 + 25)^4 \\
 \mathbf{2565726409} & := (2 + 56 - 5 - 7 - 2 + 6 - 4 - 09)^6 \\
 & := (-2 + 56 - 5 - 7 + 2 + 6 - 4 - 09)^6 \\
 & := (2 + 56 - 5 - 7 + 2 - 6 + 4 - 09)^6 \\
 & := (2 + 5 - 6 + 57 - 2 - 6 - 4 - 09)^6 \\
 & := (-2 + 5 - 6 + 57 + 2 - 6 - 4 - 09)^6 \\
 & := (-25 + 6 + 57 - 2 + 6 + 4 - 09)^6 \\
 & := (-25 + 6 - 5 + 72 - 6 + 4 - 09)^6 \\
 & := (-25 - 6 - 5 + 72 + 6 + 4 - 09)^6 \\
 & := (2 + 56 - 5 + 7 + 2 + 6 - 40 + 9)^6 \\
 & := (2 + 5 - 6 + 57 - 26 - 4 + 09)^6 \\
 & := (2 - 5 + 6 + 57 + 2 + 6 - 40 + 9)^6 \\
 & := (2 + 5 + 6 - 5 + 72 + 6 - 40 - 9)^6 \\
 & := (2 - 5 + 6 + 5 + 72 + 6 - 40 - 9)^6 \\
 & := (-2 + 5 - 6 + 5 + 72 - 6 - 40 + 9)^6 \\
 & := (25 + 65 - 72 + 6 + 4 + 09)^6 \\
 & := (25 - 6 + 57 - 26 - 4 - 09)^6 \\
 & := (25 - 6 - 57 + 2 + 64 + 09)^6 \\
 & := (25 - 6 + 57 - 2 - 6 - 40 + 9)^6 \\
 & := (25 + 6 + 5 - 72 + 64 + 09)^6 \\
 & := (2 + 56 - 5 + 7 + 26 - 40 - 9)^6 \\
 & := (-2 + 56 - 5 - 7 + 26 - 40 + 9)^6 \\
 & := (2 + 5 + 65 - 72 + 6 + 40 - 9)^6 \\
 & := (-2 - 5 - 65 + 72 + 6 + 40 - 9)^6 \\
 & := (2 - 5 + 6 + 57 + 26 - 40 - 9)^6 \\
 & := (-25 - 65 + 72 + 64 - 09)^6 \\
 & := (-25 - 65 + 72 + 6 + 40 + 9)^6 \\
 & := (25 - 6 - 57 + 26 + 40 + 9)^6 \\
 \mathbf{2576987811} & := (-2 + 576 + 9 + 8 + 781 - 1)^3 \\
 \mathbf{2593941624} & := (25 + 939 + 416 - 2 - 4)^3 \\
 \mathbf{2608451329} & := (-260 + 8 - 4 + 51329)^2 \\
 \mathbf{2608757776} & := (260 + 8 + 7 - 57 + 7 + 7 - 6)^4 \\
 & := (2 + 60 + 87 + 57 + 7 + 7 + 6)^4 \\
 & := (-2 + 60 + 87 + 5 + 77 - 7 + 6)^4 \\
 & := (-2 + 60 + 87 + 5 - 7 + 77 + 6)^4 \\
 & := (-2 + 60 + 87 + 5 + 7 - 7 + 76)^4 \\
 & := (-2 + 60 + 87 + 5 - 7 + 7 + 76)^4 \\
 & := (-260 - 8 - 7 + 577 - 76)^4 \\
 \mathbf{2624512900} & := (-2 - 62 + 4 + 51290 + 0)^2 \\
 \mathbf{2630151225} & := (-2 + 63 - 01 + 51225)^2 \\
 \mathbf{2639514968} & := (-2 - 6 - 3 - 95 + 1496 - 8)^3 \\
 \mathbf{2645248887} & := (-26 + 4 + 524 + 888 - 7)^3 \\
 & := (2 - 6 + 452 + 48 + 887)^3 \\
 \mathbf{2647514116} & := (26 + 4 + 7 + 51411 + 6)^2 \\
 \mathbf{2649057961} & := (-2 - 6490 + 57961)^2 \\
 \mathbf{2655134784} & := (265 + 51347 - 84)^2 \\
 \mathbf{2655237841} & := (265 + 5 - 23 - 7 - 8 - 4 - 1)^4 \\
 & := (265 - 5 - 23 - 7 - 8 + 4 + 1)^4 \\
 & := (265 + 5 + 2 - 3 + 7 - 8 - 41)^4 \\
 & := (265 - 5 + 23 - 7 - 8 - 41)^4 \\
 & := (2 - 6 - 55 + 237 + 8 + 41)^4 \\
 & := (2 - 655 + 2 + 37 + 841)^4 \\
 \mathbf{2656741625} & := (2 + 6 + 5 + 6 + 741 + 625)^3 \\
 \mathbf{2668267603} & := (26 + 682 + 676 + 03)^3 \\
 \mathbf{2691419471} & := (2 - 6 + 914 + 1 + 9 + 471)^3 \\
 \mathbf{2694751921} & := (-2 - 6 + 9 - 4 - 7 + 51921)^2 \\
 & := (2 - 6 - 9 - 4 + 7 + 51921)^2 \\
 \mathbf{2697451969} & := (-26 - 9 + 7 - 4 + 51969)^2 \\
 \mathbf{2702336256} & := (270 - 2 - 33 + 6 - 2 - 5 - 6)^4 \\
 & := (270 - 2 - 33 - 6 - 2 - 5 + 6)^4 \\
 & := (270 - 2 - 3 - 36 - 2 - 5 + 6)^4 \\
 & := (2 + 7 + 02 - 33 - 6 + 256)^4 \\
 & := (2 + 7 + 02 - 3 - 36 + 256)^4 \\
 & := (270 - 2 + 33 - 62 - 5 - 6)^4 \\
 & := (-2 + 70 + 233 - 62 - 5 - 6)^4 \\
 & := (2 - 70 + 233 + 62 - 5 + 6)^4 \\
 \mathbf{2706784157} & := (2 + 7 + 067 + 8 + 4 + 1 - 5 - 7)^5
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 &:= (2+7+067+8-4-1+5-7)^5 & &:= (-270-67-8+415+7)^5 \\
 &:= (-2+7+067+8-4-1-5+7)^5 & &:= (-2+706-784+157)^5 \\
 &:= (2-7+067+8+4+1-5+7)^5 & & \mathbf{2715452100} := (-2-7+15+4+52100)^2 \\
 &:= (2-7+067+8-4-1+5+7)^5 & & \mathbf{2726397773} := (-2+726-3-97+773)^3 \\
 &:= (2+7+067-8-4+1+5+7)^5 & & \mathbf{2750058481} := (275-005+8-48-1)^4 \\
 &:= (-2+7-06+7+84-1-5-7)^5 & & &:= (2+7+50+05+84+81)^4 \\
 &:= (-2+7+06-7+84+1-5-7)^5 & & \mathbf{2761677827} := (-2+7+616+7+782-7)^3 \\
 &:= (-2-7+06+7+84+1-5-7)^5 & & &:= (-2+7+616-7+782+7)^3 \\
 &:= (2+7-06-7+84-1+5-7)^5 & & &:= (-2-7+616+7+782+7)^3 \\
 &:= (2-7-06+7+84-1+5-7)^5 & & \mathbf{2767587264} := (-2-7+675+8+726+4)^3 \\
 &:= (2-7+06-7+84+1+5-7)^5 & & \mathbf{2773505125} := (2+773+505+125)^3 \\
 &:= (-2+7-06-7+84-1-5+7)^5 & & \mathbf{2778554944} := (-2778+55494-4)^2 \\
 &:= (-2-7-06+7+84-1-5+7)^5 & & \mathbf{2779431416} := (2-7-7+9-4-3+1416)^3 \\
 &:= (-2-7+06-7+84+1-5+7)^5 & & &:= (-2+7-7-9+4-3+1416)^3 \\
 &:= (2-7-06-7+84-1+5+7)^5 & & &:= (-2-7+7-9+4-3+1416)^3 \\
 &:= (27+067-8+4-1-5-7)^5 & & &:= (-27+7+9+4-3+1416)^3 \\
 &:= (27+06+7+8+41-5-7)^5 & & &:= (2779+43-1416)^3 \\
 &:= (27+06-7+8+41-5+7)^5 & & \mathbf{2785366143} := (2+785+3+6+614-3)^3 \\
 &:= (-2+70+6+7-8-4+15-7)^5 & & &:= (2+785-3+6+614+3)^3 \\
 &:= (2+70-6+7-8+4+15-7)^5 & & \mathbf{2797260929} := (-2+797-2+609-2+9)^3 \\
 &:= (-2+70+6+7+8-4-15+7)^5 & & \mathbf{2798410000} := (279-8-41+0000)^4 \\
 &:= (2+70-6+7+8+4-15+7)^5 & & \mathbf{2800526400} := (280+052640+0)^2 \\
 &:= (-2+70+6-7-8-4+15+7)^5 & & \mathbf{2805291225} := (28+052912+25)^2 \\
 &:= (2+70-6-7-8+4+15+7)^5 & & &:= (-2+80+52912-25)^2 \\
 &:= (-2+7+06+78-4-15+7)^5 & & \mathbf{2815166528} := (2+815+1+66+528)^3 \\
 &:= (2+7-06+78+4-15+7)^5 & & \mathbf{2821151997} := (2-8-2-1+1519-97)^3 \\
 &:= (-27+067+8+41-5-7)^5 & & &:= (-2-8+2-1+1519-97)^3 \\
 &:= (2+70+67-8+4-1-57)^5 & & \mathbf{2822053129} := (2-8+2-2+053129)^2 \\
 &:= (2+70+6+7+8+41-57)^5 & & &:= (2-8-2+2+053129)^2 \\
 &:= (-2+70-6+7-8-41+57)^5 & & &:= (-2-8+2+2+053129)^2 \\
 &:= (-2-7-067-8+4+157)^5 & & &:= (-28+22+053129)^2 \\
 &:= (2+7+06+78+41-57)^5 & & &:= (-28+2+20+53129)^2 \\
 &:= (-2+7+06-7-84+157)^5 & & \mathbf{2827145944} := (-28-2-7+1459-4-4)^3 \\
 &:= (-2-7+06+7-84+157)^5 & & &:= (2+827-1-4+594-4)^3 \\
 &:= (2-706+784-1+5-7)^5 & & &:= (-2-8-27+1459-4-4)^3 \\
 &:= (-2-706+784-1-5+7)^5 & & &:= (2-8-2+7+1459-44)^3 \\
 &:= (-2+70-67+84-15+7)^5 & & &:= (-2-8+2+7+1459-44)^3 \\
 &:= (2+70+67-84+15+7)^5 & & &:= (-28+27+1459-44)^3
 \end{aligned}$$

2845178713 := (28 + 4 + 517 + 871 - 3) ³	:= (2 + 8 + 8 + 7 + 1 + 7 + 43 - 6 + 8) ⁵
2847396321 := (284 + 7 - 3 + 9 - 63 - 2 - 1) ⁴	:= (2 + 8 + 8 + 7 - 1 - 7 - 4 - 3 + 68) ⁵
:= (2 - 8 + 4 - 73 - 9 - 6 + 321) ⁴	:= (2 + 8 + 8 - 7 - 1 + 7 - 4 - 3 + 68) ⁵
:= (-2 - 8 - 4 - 73 - 9 + 6 + 321) ⁴	:= (2 + 8 - 8 + 7 + 1 + 7 - 4 - 3 + 68) ⁵
:= (-2 + 8 - 4 + 7 - 3 - 96 + 321) ⁴	:= (2 - 8 + 8 + 7 + 1 + 7 - 4 - 3 + 68) ⁵
:= (-2 + 8 + 4 - 7 + 3 - 96 + 321) ⁴	:= (-2 + 8 - 8 + 7 - 1 + 7 - 4 + 3 + 68) ⁵
:= (284 + 7 + 3 - 96 + 32 + 1) ⁴	:= (-2 - 8 + 8 + 7 - 1 + 7 - 4 + 3 + 68) ⁵
:= (-28 - 4 - 73 + 9 + 6 + 321) ⁴	:= (2 + 8 + 8 - 7 - 1 - 7 + 4 + 3 + 68) ⁵
:= (2 + 84 + 73 + 96 - 3 - 21) ⁴	:= (2 + 8 - 8 + 7 + 1 - 7 + 4 + 3 + 68) ⁵
:= (-2 - 8 - 47 - 39 + 6 + 321) ⁴	:= (2 - 8 + 8 + 7 + 1 - 7 + 4 + 3 + 68) ⁵
2853162225 := (28 + 53162 + 225) ²	:= (2 + 8 - 8 - 7 + 1 + 7 + 4 + 3 + 68) ⁵
2865353841 := (-2 - 8 + 6 + 53538 - 4 - 1) ²	:= (2 - 8 + 8 - 7 + 1 + 7 + 4 + 3 + 68) ⁵
:= (2 - 8 - 6 + 53538 + 4 - 1) ²	:= (-28 + 87 - 1 + 7 - 4 + 3 + 6 + 8) ⁵
2869341461 := (28 - 69 - 3 + 4 + 1461) ³	:= (28 + 8 + 7 - 1 + 7 + 43 - 6 - 8) ⁵
2881473967 := (-2 - 8 - 8 + 1 + 473 + 967) ³	:= (28 + 8 + 7 + 1 - 7 + 43 + 6 - 8) ⁵
:= (-2 + 8814 - 7396 + 7) ³	:= (28 + 8 - 7 + 1 + 7 + 43 + 6 - 8) ⁵
2887174368 := (-2 + 88 + 7 - 1 + 7 - 4 - 3 - 6 - 8) ⁵	:= (28 - 8 + 7 - 1 + 7 + 43 - 6 + 8) ⁵
:= (2 + 88 + 7 + 1 - 7 + 4 - 3 - 6 - 8) ⁵	:= (28 + 8 - 7 - 1 - 7 + 43 + 6 + 8) ⁵
:= (2 + 88 - 7 + 1 + 7 + 4 - 3 - 6 - 8) ⁵	:= (28 - 8 + 7 + 1 - 7 + 43 + 6 + 8) ⁵
:= (-2 + 88 + 7 - 1 - 7 + 4 + 3 - 6 - 8) ⁵	:= (28 - 8 - 7 + 1 + 7 + 43 + 6 + 8) ⁵
:= (-2 + 88 - 7 - 1 + 7 + 4 + 3 - 6 - 8) ⁵	:= (-2 - 8 - 8 + 71 - 7 + 4 + 36 - 8) ⁵
:= (-2 + 88 + 7 + 1 - 7 - 4 - 3 + 6 - 8) ⁵	:= (-2 + 8 + 8 + 7 + 17 - 4 + 36 + 8) ⁵
:= (-2 + 88 - 7 + 1 + 7 - 4 - 3 + 6 - 8) ⁵	:= (-2 - 8 - 8 - 7 + 1 + 74 + 36 - 8) ⁵
:= (-2 + 88 - 7 + 1 - 7 + 4 + 3 + 6 - 8) ⁵	:= (-2 - 8 - 8 - 7 - 1 - 7 + 43 + 68) ⁵
:= (2 + 88 - 7 - 1 - 7 + 4 - 3 - 6 + 8) ⁵	:= (28 + 87 + 1 + 7 - 43 + 6 - 8) ⁵
:= (2 + 88 - 7 + 1 - 7 - 4 + 3 - 6 + 8) ⁵	:= (28 + 87 - 1 - 7 - 43 + 6 + 8) ⁵
:= (-2 + 88 - 7 - 1 - 7 - 4 - 3 + 6 + 8) ⁵	:= (28 + 8 - 7 + 17 + 4 + 36 - 8) ⁵
:= (-2 + 8 + 87 - 1 + 7 - 4 - 3 - 6 - 8) ⁵	:= (28 - 8 - 7 + 17 + 4 + 36 + 8) ⁵
:= (2 + 8 + 87 + 1 - 7 + 4 - 3 - 6 - 8) ⁵	:= (-28 + 8 - 7 + 1 - 7 + 43 + 68) ⁵
:= (-2 + 8 + 87 - 1 - 7 + 4 + 3 - 6 - 8) ⁵	:= (-2 + 88 - 71 + 74 + 3 - 6 - 8) ⁵
:= (-2 - 8 + 87 + 1 + 7 + 4 + 3 - 6 - 8) ⁵	:= (-2 + 88 + 71 - 74 - 3 + 6 - 8) ⁵
:= (-2 + 8 + 87 + 1 - 7 - 4 - 3 + 6 - 8) ⁵	:= (2 - 88 + 7 + 174 - 3 - 6 - 8) ⁵
:= (2 - 8 + 87 - 1 + 7 - 4 - 3 + 6 - 8) ⁵	:= (-2 - 88 - 7 + 174 + 3 + 6 - 8) ⁵
:= (2 - 8 + 87 - 1 - 7 + 4 + 3 + 6 - 8) ⁵	:= (-2 + 88 + 7 + 17 - 4 - 36 + 8) ⁵
:= (-2 - 8 + 87 - 1 + 7 - 4 - 3 - 6 + 8) ⁵	:= (2 + 88 + 7 - 1 + 7 + 43 - 68) ⁵
:= (2 - 8 + 87 + 1 - 7 + 4 - 3 - 6 + 8) ⁵	:= (-2 - 8 - 87 + 174 + 3 + 6 - 8) ⁵
:= (-2 - 8 + 87 - 1 - 7 + 4 + 3 - 6 + 8) ⁵	:= (-2 + 8 + 87 + 17 - 4 - 36 + 8) ⁵
:= (-2 - 8 + 87 + 1 - 7 - 4 - 3 + 6 + 8) ⁵	:= (2 + 8 + 87 - 1 + 7 + 43 - 68) ⁵

$$\begin{aligned}
 & := (-2 + 8 - 8 + 71 + 74 + 3 - 68)^5 \\
 & := (-2 - 8 + 8 + 71 + 74 + 3 - 68)^5 \\
 & := (-2 - 8 - 8 - 7 + 174 - 3 - 68)^5 \\
 & := (-28 + 87 + 1 - 7 - 43 + 68)^5 \\
 & := (288 - 71 - 74 + 3 - 68)^5 \\
 & := (-288 - 71 - 7 + 436 + 8)^5 \\
 \mathbf{2897022976} & := (-2 + 8 - 9 + 7 + 0229 - 7 + 6)^4 \\
 & := (-2 + 8 - 9 - 7 + 0229 + 7 + 6)^4 \\
 & := (28 + 97 + 02 + 2 + 97 + 6)^4 \\
 & := (2 + 89 + 70 + 2 + 2 - 9 + 76)^4 \\
 & := (2 + 8 + 97 + 022 + 97 + 6)^4 \\
 & := (2 + 8 - 9 - 70 - 2 + 297 + 6)^4 \\
 & := (-2 + 8 - 9 - 70 + 2 + 297 + 6)^4 \\
 & := (28 + 97 + 022 + 9 + 76)^4 \\
 & := (28 - 97 - 02 + 297 + 6)^4 \\
 & := (28 + 97 + 02 + 29 + 76)^4 \\
 & := (28 + 9 + 70 + 22 + 97 + 6)^4 \\
 & := (-2 + 8 - 9 - 70 + 229 + 76)^4 \\
 \mathbf{2916540025} & := (2 - 9 - 1 + 6 + 54002 + 5)^2 \\
 \mathbf{2918076589} & := (-2 + 918 - 076 + 589)^3 \\
 \mathbf{2928541456} & := (-29 - 2 + 8 + 54145 - 6)^2 \\
 & := (-29 + 2 - 8 + 54145 + 6)^2 \\
 & := (2 - 9 - 28 + 54145 + 6)^2 \\
 \mathbf{2930345991} & := (2 + 93 + 0345 + 991)^3 \\
 \mathbf{2942649737} & := (-2 + 942 + 6 + 497 - 3 - 7)^3 \\
 \mathbf{2947295521} & := (2 + 94 + 72 + 9 + 55 + 2 - 1)^4 \\
 & := (2 + 94 + 72 + 9 + 5 + 52 - 1)^4 \\
 & := (2 + 94 - 7 - 2 + 95 + 52 - 1)^4 \\
 & := (-2 + 94 - 7 + 2 + 95 + 52 - 1)^4 \\
 & := (2 - 9 - 47 + 295 - 5 - 2 - 1)^4 \\
 & := (-2 - 9 - 47 + 295 - 5 + 2 - 1)^4 \\
 & := (2 + 9 + 4 + 72 + 95 + 52 - 1)^4 \\
 & := (-2 + 94 + 72 + 95 - 5 - 21)^4 \\
 & := (2 + 9 - 47 + 295 - 5 - 21)^4 \\
 \mathbf{2954357316} & := (-2 + 9 + 54357 - 3 - 1 - 6)^2 \\
 & := (-2 - 9 + 54357 + 3 - 1 + 6)^2 \\
 & := (2 - 9 + 54357 - 3 + 1 + 6)^2 \\
 \mathbf{2955444496} & := (2 + 9 + 5 + 54444 - 96)^2
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 \mathbf{2965455936} & := (2 - 96 + 54559 - 3 - 6)^2 \\
 \mathbf{2966545156} & := (2 + 9 - 66 + 54515 + 6)^2 \\
 \mathbf{2979767519} & := (-297 + 976 + 751 + 9)^3 \\
 \mathbf{2995482361} & := (2 - 99 + 54823 + 6 - 1)^2 \\
 \mathbf{2998219536} & := (2 + 9 + 9 + 8 + 2 + 195 + 3 + 6)^4 \\
 & := (299 - 8 - 2 + 1 - 9 - 53 + 6)^4 \\
 & := (29 + 98 + 2 + 1 + 95 + 3 + 6)^4 \\
 & := (29 + 9 + 8 + 2 + 195 - 3 - 6)^4 \\
 & := (29 - 9 + 8 + 2 + 195 + 3 + 6)^4 \\
 & := (-2 + 99 + 82 - 1 + 9 + 53 - 6)^4 \\
 & := (2 + 99 + 82 + 1 - 9 + 53 + 6)^4 \\
 & := (2 + 99 + 82 + 1 + 9 + 5 + 36)^4 \\
 & := (2 + 99 + 8 + 21 + 95 + 3 + 6)^4 \\
 & := (2 + 9 + 98 + 21 + 95 + 3 + 6)^4 \\
 & := (2 + 9 + 9 + 82 + 1 + 95 + 36)^4 \\
 & := (299 - 82 + 19 - 5 - 3 + 6)^4 \\
 & := (29 + 98 + 21 + 95 - 3 - 6)^4 \\
 & := (29 - 9 + 82 + 1 + 95 + 36)^4 \\
 & := (29 + 9 + 8 + 219 + 5 - 36)^4 \\
 \mathbf{2998442888} & := (-2 + 998 - 442 + 888)^3 \\
 \mathbf{3010936384} & := (30 - 1 + 09 + 3 + 6 + 3 - 8 - 4)^6 \\
 & := (30 + 1 + 09 + 3 - 6 - 3 + 8 - 4)^6 \\
 & := (30 + 1 + 09 - 3 - 6 + 3 + 8 - 4)^6 \\
 & := (30 + 1 - 09 + 3 + 6 + 3 + 8 - 4)^6 \\
 & := (30 - 1 + 09 - 3 - 6 - 3 + 8 + 4)^6 \\
 & := (30 - 1 - 09 + 3 + 6 - 3 + 8 + 4)^6 \\
 & := (30 - 1 - 09 - 3 + 6 + 3 + 8 + 4)^6 \\
 & := (3 + 010 + 9 + 3 + 6 + 3 + 8 - 4)^6 \\
 & := (3 - 01 + 09 + 36 + 3 - 8 - 4)^6 \\
 & := (3 + 01 - 09 + 36 + 3 + 8 - 4)^6 \\
 & := (3 - 01 - 09 + 36 - 3 + 8 + 4)^6 \\
 & := (-3 - 01 - 09 + 36 + 3 + 8 + 4)^6 \\
 & := (3 + 01 + 09 - 3 - 6 + 38 - 4)^6 \\
 & := (-3 + 01 + 09 + 3 - 6 + 38 - 4)^6 \\
 & := (3 + 01 - 09 + 3 + 6 + 38 - 4)^6 \\
 & := (-3 - 01 + 09 - 3 - 6 + 38 + 4)^6 \\
 & := (3 - 01 - 09 - 3 + 6 + 38 + 4)^6 \\
 & := (-3 - 01 - 09 + 3 + 6 + 38 + 4)^6
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 & := (-30 - 1 - 09 + 3 + 63 + 8 + 4)^6 \\
 & := (-30 - 1 - 09 + 3 - 6 - 3 + 84)^6 \\
 & := (-30 - 1 - 09 - 3 - 6 + 3 + 84)^6 \\
 & := (3 - 010 - 9 + 3 + 63 - 8 - 4)^6 \\
 & := (3 + 01 + 093 - 63 + 8 - 4)^6 \\
 & := (-3 - 01 + 093 - 63 + 8 + 4)^6 \\
 & := (3 - 01 - 09 - 36 - 3 + 84)^6 \\
 & := (-3 - 01 - 09 - 36 + 3 + 84)^6 \\
 & := (-30 - 10 + 93 - 6 + 3 - 8 - 4)^6 \\
 & := (30 - 10 - 9 + 36 + 3 - 8 - 4)^6 \\
 & := (30 + 1 + 09 - 36 + 38 - 4)^6 \\
 & := (-30 - 1 - 09 + 36 + 38 + 4)^6 \\
 & := (30 - 1 - 09 - 3 - 63 + 84)^6 \\
 & := (3 - 010 + 93 - 6 - 38 - 4)^6 \\
 & := (30 - 10 + 93 - 63 - 8 - 4)^6 \\
 & := (30 - 10 + 93 + 6 + 3 - 84)^6 \\
 & := (3 - 0109 - 3 + 63 + 84)^6 \\
 & := (-3 - 0109 + 3 + 63 + 84)^6 \\
 & := (-301 - 09 - 36 + 384)^6 \\
 & := (30 - 109 + 36 - 3 + 84)^6 \\
 \mathbf{3029952025} & := (3029 - 9 + 52025)^2 \\
 \mathbf{3067586677} & := (30 - 6 + 758 - 6 + 677)^3 \\
 \mathbf{3077056399} & := (-3 + 07 + 7 + 05 + 63 + 9 - 9)^5 \\
 & := (-3 + 07 + 7 + 05 + 63 - 9 + 9)^5 \\
 & := (3 + 07 - 7 - 05 + 63 + 9 + 9)^5 \\
 & := (3 - 07 + 7 - 05 + 63 + 9 + 9)^5 \\
 & := (-30 + 77 + 05 + 6 + 3 + 9 + 9)^5 \\
 & := (30 - 7 + 70 - 5 + 6 + 3 - 9 - 9)^5 \\
 & := (30 - 7 + 70 - 5 - 6 - 3 + 9 - 9)^5 \\
 & := (30 - 7 + 70 - 5 - 6 - 3 - 9 + 9)^5 \\
 & := (-30 + 7 + 70 + 5 + 6 + 3 + 9 + 9)^5 \\
 & := (30 + 7 + 7 + 056 - 3 - 9 - 9)^5 \\
 & := (30 + 7 - 7 - 05 + 6 + 39 + 9)^5 \\
 & := (30 - 7 + 7 - 05 + 6 + 39 + 9)^5 \\
 & := (-30 + 7 + 7 + 05 - 6 - 3 + 99)^5 \\
 & := (-3 - 07 + 70 - 5 - 6 + 39 - 9)^5 \\
 & := (-30 - 7 + 70 - 56 + 3 + 99)^5 \\
 & := (-3 + 07 + 705 - 639 + 9)^5 \\
 & := (307 - 70 - 56 - 3 - 99)^5 \\
 \mathbf{3102044416} & := (31 + 0204 + 4 + 4 - 1 - 6)^4 \\
 & := (3 - 10 + 204 + 44 + 1 - 6)^4 \\
 & := (3 - 10 + 204 + 4 + 41 - 6)^4 \\
 & := (3 + 1 + 0204 + 44 - 16)^4 \\
 & := (3 - 10 - 204 + 441 + 6)^4 \\
 \mathbf{3125592649} & := (-3 - 1 - 2 + 55926 - 4 - 9)^2 \\
 \mathbf{3137785344} & := (-3 + 1377 + 85 - 3 + 4 + 4)^3 \\
 \mathbf{3144219625} & := (3 + 1442 + 19 - 6 + 2 + 5)^3 \\
 \mathbf{3154956561} & := (315 - 4 - 9 - 5 - 65 + 6 - 1)^4 \\
 & := (315 - 4 - 9 + 5 - 65 - 6 + 1)^4 \\
 & := (315 - 4 - 9 - 5 + 6 - 5 - 61)^4 \\
 & := (-3 + 154 + 9 + 5 + 65 + 6 + 1)^4 \\
 & := (-3 + 154 + 9 + 5 + 6 + 5 + 61)^4 \\
 & := (-3 + 15 + 4 + 95 + 65 + 61)^4 \\
 \mathbf{3157114563} & := (3 + 1571 + 1 - 45 - 63)^3 \\
 \mathbf{3176523000} & := (3 + 1765 + 2 - 300 + 0)^3 \\
 \mathbf{3208542736} & := (3 + 208 + 5 + 4 + 2 + 7 + 3 + 6)^4 \\
 & := (320 + 8 - 5 - 4 - 2 - 73 - 6)^4 \\
 & := (320 - 8 - 5 - 4 + 2 - 73 + 6)^4 \\
 & := (-32 - 08 - 5 + 4 + 273 + 6)^4 \\
 & := (3 + 208 - 5 + 42 - 7 + 3 - 6)^4 \\
 & := (-3 + 208 - 5 + 42 - 7 - 3 + 6)^4 \\
 & := (3 + 208 + 5 + 4 + 27 - 3 - 6)^4 \\
 & := (-3 + 208 + 5 + 4 + 27 + 3 - 6)^4 \\
 & := (3 + 208 - 5 - 4 + 27 + 3 + 6)^4 \\
 & := (3 + 2 + 08 - 54 + 273 + 6)^4 \\
 & := (320 + 8 - 54 - 27 - 3 - 6)^4 \\
 & := (320 + 8 - 5 - 42 - 7 - 36)^4 \\
 & := (32 + 085 + 42 + 73 + 6)^4 \\
 & := (3 + 208 - 54 + 2 + 73 + 6)^4 \\
 & := (3 + 208 + 54 + 2 + 7 - 36)^4 \\
 & := (-3 + 20 + 8 - 54 + 273 - 6)^4 \\
 \mathbf{3215457025} & := (-321 + 5 - 4 + 57025)^2 \\
 \mathbf{3215578176} & := (-3 + 2 + 1557 - 81 + 7 - 6)^3 \\
 & := (3 - 2 + 1557 - 81 - 7 + 6)^3 \\
 \mathbf{3240569476} & := (-3 - 24 + 056947 + 6)^2 \\
 \mathbf{3245694841} & := (32 - 4 + 56948 - 4 - 1)^2
 \end{aligned}$$

3248367641 := (3 - 2 - 4 + 836 + 7 + 641) ³	:= (-3 + 4 + 04 + 8 - 2 + 5 + 4 - 4 + 7) ⁷
3249570025 := (-3 - 2 + 4 + 9 + 57002 - 5) ²	:= (3 + 4 + 04 + 8 + 2 - 5 - 4 + 4 + 7) ⁷
3261545587 := (-3 - 2 - 6 + 1545 - 58 + 7) ³	:= (-3 + 4 + 04 + 8 - 2 + 5 - 4 + 4 + 7) ⁷
3262808641 := (326 - 2 - 80 - 8 + 6 - 4 + 1) ⁴	:= (3 + 4 - 04 + 8 + 2 - 5 + 4 + 4 + 7) ⁷
:= (326 + 2 - 80 - 8 - 6 + 4 + 1) ⁴	:= (3 - 4 + 04 + 8 + 2 - 5 + 4 + 4 + 7) ⁷
:= (326 + 2 - 8 - 086 + 4 + 1) ⁴	:= (-3 + 4 - 04 + 8 - 2 + 5 + 4 + 4 + 7) ⁷
:= (-32 - 6 + 280 + 8 - 6 - 4 - 1) ⁴	:= (-3 - 4 + 04 + 8 - 2 + 5 + 4 + 4 + 7) ⁷
3268147904 := (-3 - 2 + 6 + 8 + 1479 - 04) ³	:= (-3 + 40 - 4 + 8 + 2 - 5 - 4 - 4 - 7) ⁷
:= (-3 + 2 - 6 + 8 + 1479 + 04) ³	:= (3 + 40 - 4 - 8 + 2 + 5 - 4 - 4 - 7) ⁷
:= (3 + 2 + 681 + 4 + 790 + 4) ³	:= (-3 + 40 + 4 - 8 + 2 - 5 + 4 - 4 - 7) ⁷
3276800000 := (3 + 2 + 7 + 68 + 00000) ⁵	:= (-3 + 40 + 4 - 8 + 2 - 5 - 4 + 4 - 7) ⁷
:= (-3 + 2 + 7 - 6 + 80 + 0000) ⁵	:= (-3 + 40 - 4 - 8 + 2 - 5 + 4 + 4 - 7) ⁷
:= (3 - 2 - 7 + 6 + 80 + 0000) ⁵	:= (3 + 40 - 4 - 8 - 2 - 5 - 4 - 4 + 7) ⁷
3293956449 := (3 + 2 + 939 + 56449) ²	:= (-3 - 4 + 048 + 2 - 5 - 4 - 4 - 7) ⁷
3301293169 := (-3 + 30 + 1293 + 169) ³	:= (-3 + 4 + 04 + 8 + 25 - 4 - 4 - 7) ⁷
3311657209 := (331 + 1 + 6 + 57209) ²	:= (-3 + 4 - 04 + 8 + 25 + 4 - 4 - 7) ⁷
3314613771 := (-33 + 146 + 1377 + 1) ³	:= (-3 - 4 + 04 + 8 + 25 + 4 - 4 - 7) ⁷
3348071936 := (33 - 480 + 7 + 1936) ³	:= (-3 + 4 - 04 + 8 + 25 - 4 + 4 - 7) ⁷
3352757409 := (-33 + 527 + 57409) ²	:= (-3 - 4 + 04 + 8 + 25 - 4 + 4 - 7) ⁷
3357970704 := (-33 + 57970 + 7 + 04) ²	:= (-3 + 4 + 04 - 8 + 25 + 4 + 4 - 7) ⁷
3361517992 := (-33 - 6 + 1517 + 9 + 9 + 2) ³	:= (-3 - 4 - 04 + 8 + 25 + 4 + 4 - 7) ⁷
:= (-3 - 36 + 1517 + 9 + 9 + 2) ³	:= (-3 + 4 - 04 - 8 + 2 - 5 + 44 - 7) ⁷
:= (-3 - 3 - 6 + 1 + 517 + 992) ³	:= (-3 - 4 + 04 - 8 + 2 - 5 + 44 - 7) ⁷
3364580025 := (3 + 3 + 6 - 4 + 58002 - 5) ²	:= (3 - 4 - 04 - 8 - 2 - 5 - 4 + 47) ⁷
:= (3 - 3 - 6 + 4 + 58002 + 5) ²	:= (-34 + 04 + 8 + 2 + 54 - 4 - 7) ⁷
:= (-3 + 3 - 6 + 4 + 58002 + 5) ²	:= (-34 - 04 + 8 + 2 + 54 + 4 - 7) ⁷
3373402561 := (3 - 3 - 7 - 3 - 4 + 0256 - 1) ⁴	:= (3 - 40 + 48 + 2 - 5 + 4 + 4 + 7) ⁷
:= (-3 + 3 - 7 - 3 - 4 + 0256 - 1) ⁴	:= (-3 - 40 + 48 - 2 + 5 + 4 + 4 + 7) ⁷
:= (-3 - 3 - 7 + 3 - 4 + 0256 - 1) ⁴	:= (-3 - 40 + 4 + 82 - 5 - 4 - 4 - 7) ⁷
:= (337 + 3 - 40 - 2 - 56 - 1) ⁴	:= (-3 - 40 - 4 + 82 - 5 + 4 - 4 - 7) ⁷
:= (337 - 3 - 40 + 2 - 56 + 1) ⁴	:= (-3 - 40 - 4 + 82 - 5 - 4 + 4 - 7) ⁷
:= (-33 - 7 + 340 - 2 - 56 - 1) ⁴	:= (3 + 40 + 4 + 8 - 25 + 4 - 4 - 7) ⁷
:= (-3 - 37 + 340 - 2 - 56 - 1) ⁴	:= (3 + 40 + 4 + 8 - 25 - 4 + 4 - 7) ⁷
:= (-3 - 3 - 7 + 340 - 25 - 61) ⁴	:= (3 + 40 - 4 + 8 - 25 + 4 + 4 - 7) ⁷
:= (-33 - 73 + 402 - 56 + 1) ⁴	:= (-3 + 40 + 4 + 8 - 25 - 4 - 4 + 7) ⁷
3395290527 := (33 + 952 - 9 + 0527) ³	:= (-3 + 40 - 4 + 8 - 25 + 4 - 4 + 7) ⁷
3404825447 := (3 + 4 + 04 + 8 - 2 + 5 + 4 + 4 - 7) ⁷	:= (-3 + 40 - 4 + 8 - 25 - 4 + 4 + 7) ⁷
:= (3 + 4 + 04 + 8 + 2 - 5 + 4 - 4 + 7) ⁷	:= (-3 + 40 + 4 - 8 - 25 + 4 + 4 + 7) ⁷

$$\begin{aligned}
 &:= (3 - 40 + 4 + 8 + 2 - 5 + 44 + 7)^7 \\
 &:= (-3 - 40 + 4 + 8 - 2 + 5 + 44 + 7)^7 \\
 &:= (3 - 40 + 4 + 8 + 2 - 5 + 4 + 47)^7 \\
 &:= (-3 - 40 + 4 + 8 - 2 + 5 + 4 + 47)^7 \\
 &:= (3 + 4 + 048 - 25 + 4 - 4 - 7)^7 \\
 &:= (3 + 4 + 048 - 25 - 4 + 4 - 7)^7 \\
 &:= (3 - 4 + 048 - 25 + 4 + 4 - 7)^7 \\
 &:= (-3 + 4 + 048 - 25 - 4 - 4 + 7)^7 \\
 &:= (-3 - 4 + 048 - 25 + 4 - 4 + 7)^7 \\
 &:= (-3 - 4 + 048 - 25 - 4 + 4 + 7)^7 \\
 &:= (-3 + 4 - 04 + 82 - 5 - 44 - 7)^7 \\
 &:= (-3 - 4 + 04 + 82 - 5 - 44 - 7)^7 \\
 &:= (-3 + 4 - 04 + 82 - 5 - 4 - 47)^7 \\
 &:= (-3 - 4 + 04 + 82 - 5 - 4 - 47)^7 \\
 &:= (-3 - 4 + 04 + 82 - 5 - 4 - 47)^7 \\
 &:= (-3 - 4 - 04 + 82 - 5 + 4 - 47)^7 \\
 &:= (3 + 4 - 04 + 8 - 25 + 44 - 7)^7 \\
 &:= (3 - 4 + 04 + 8 - 25 + 44 - 7)^7 \\
 &:= (-3 + 4 + 04 - 8 - 25 + 44 + 7)^7 \\
 &:= (-3 - 4 - 04 + 8 - 25 + 44 + 7)^7 \\
 &:= (-3 + 4 - 04 + 8 - 25 - 4 + 47)^7 \\
 &:= (-3 - 4 + 04 + 8 - 25 - 4 + 47)^7 \\
 &:= (-3 + 4 + 04 - 8 - 25 + 4 + 47)^7 \\
 &:= (-3 - 4 - 04 + 8 - 25 + 4 + 47)^7 \\
 &:= (34 + 048 - 2 - 54 + 4 - 7)^7 \\
 &:= (-3 - 40 + 48 + 25 + 4 - 4 - 7)^7 \\
 &:= (-3 - 40 + 48 + 25 - 4 + 4 - 7)^7 \\
 &:= (-3 + 40 - 48 + 2 - 5 + 44 - 7)^7 \\
 &:= (-3 + 40 + 4 + 8 + 25 - 44 - 7)^7 \\
 &:= (-3 - 40 - 4 + 8 + 25 + 44 - 7)^7 \\
 &:= (-3 + 40 + 4 + 8 + 25 - 4 - 47)^7 \\
 &:= (-3 + 40 - 4 + 8 + 25 + 4 - 47)^7 \\
 &:= (-3 + 4 + 048 + 25 - 44 - 7)^7 \\
 &:= (-3 + 4 + 048 + 25 - 4 - 47)^7 \\
 &:= (-3 - 4 + 048 + 25 + 4 - 47)^7 \\
 &:= (-34 + 048 + 2 + 54 - 47)^7 \\
 &:= (3 - 40 + 48 - 25 + 44 - 7)^7 \\
 &:= (-3 + 40 + 48 - 25 - 44 + 7)^7 \\
 &:= (3 + 40 + 48 - 25 + 4 - 47)^7
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 &:= (-3 - 40 + 48 - 25 - 4 + 47)^7 \\
 &:= (-3 - 4 + 0482 - 5 - 447)^7 \\
 &:= (-3 - 404 + 8 - 25 + 447)^7 \\
 &:= (-3 + 404 - 825 + 447)^7 \\
 &**3415584249** := (34 - 1 - 5 + 58424 - 9)^2 \\
 &**3429742096** := (342 - 97 - 4 - 2 + 09 - 6)^4 \\
 &:= (342 - 9 - 74 - 2 - 09 - 6)^4 \\
 &:= (342 + 9 - 7 - 4 - 2 - 096)^4 \\
 &:= (342 - 9 + 7 - 4 + 2 - 096)^4 \\
 &:= (-34 + 297 - 4 - 2 - 09 - 6)^4 \\
 &:= (3 + 42 - 9 + 7 - 4 + 209 - 6)^4 \\
 &:= (-3 + 42 - 9 - 7 + 4 + 209 + 6)^4 \\
 &:= (3 + 4 + 29 + 7 - 4 + 209 - 6)^4 \\
 &:= (3 - 4 + 29 + 7 + 4 + 209 - 6)^4 \\
 &:= (-3 + 4 + 29 - 7 + 4 + 209 + 6)^4 \\
 &:= (342 + 9 - 74 - 20 - 9 - 6)^4 \\
 &:= (342 - 9 - 74 - 20 + 9 - 6)^4 \\
 &:= (-34 + 297 - 4 - 20 + 9 - 6)^4 \\
 &:= (3 - 4 + 297 + 42 - 096)^4 \\
 &:= (3 + 429 - 74 - 20 - 96)^4 \\
 &**3441582225** := (-3 + 441 + 58222 + 5)^2 \\
 &**3458733721** := (3 + 4 + 58733 + 72 - 1)^2 \\
 &**3458851344** := (-34 + 58851 + 3 - 4 - 4)^2 \\
 &:= (3 - 4 + 58851 - 34 - 4)^2 \\
 &**3481590025** := (-3 + 4 + 8 - 1 + 59002 - 5)^2 \\
 &:= (3 - 4 + 8 + 1 + 59002 - 5)^2 \\
 &:= (3 + 4 - 8 - 1 + 59002 + 5)^2 \\
 &**3484156096** := (-3 - 48 + 4 + 1560 + 9 - 6)^3 \\
 &:= (3 - 48 + 4 + 1560 - 9 + 6)^3 \\
 &**3486784401** := (3 - 4 + 8 + 6 + 7 - 8 - 4 - 4 - 01)^{20} \\
 &:= (-3 + 4 + 8 - 6 + 7 + 8 - 4 - 4 - 01)^{10} \\
 &:= (3 - 4 - 8 + 6 + 7 + 8 - 4 - 4 - 01)^{20} \\
 &:= (3 + 4 - 8 + 6 + 7 - 8 + 4 - 4 - 01)^{20} \\
 &:= (-3 + 4 + 8 - 6 - 7 + 8 + 4 - 4 - 01)^{20} \\
 &:= (3 + 4 + 8 - 6 - 7 + 8 + 4 - 4 - 01)^{10} \\
 &:= (-3 - 4 + 8 - 6 + 7 + 8 + 4 - 4 - 01)^{10} \\
 &:= (3 + 4 - 8 + 6 + 7 - 8 - 4 + 4 - 01)^{20} \\
 &:= (-3 + 4 + 8 - 6 - 7 + 8 - 4 + 4 - 01)^{20}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} &:= (3+4+8-6-7+8-4+4-01)^{10} &:= (3-4+8+67+8-4+4-01)^5 \\ &:= (-3-4+8-6+7+8-4+4-01)^{10} &:= (3+4+8+67-8+4+4-01)^5 \\ &:= (-3+4+8-6+7-8+4+4-01)^{10} &:= (3+4-8+67+8+4+4-01)^5 \\ &:= (3-4-8+6+7-8+4+4-01)^{20} &:= (3+4+8-6-7+84-4-01)^5 \\ &:= (-3-4+8-6-7+8+4+4-01)^{20} &:= (-3-4+8-6+7+84-4-01)^5 \\ &:= (3-4+8-6-7+8+4+4-01)^{10} &:= (3-4+8-6-7+84+4-01)^5 \\ &:= (-3+4-8-6+7+8+4+4-01)^{10} &:= (-3+4-8-6+7+84+4-01)^5 \\ &:= (3+4+8-6-7+8-4-4+01)^{20} &:= (-3-4+8+6-7+84-4+01)^5 \\ &:= (-3+4+8+6-7+8-4-4+01)^{10} &:= (3+4-8-6+7+84-4+01)^5 \\ &:= (-3-4+8-6+7+8-4-4+01)^{20} &:= (-3+4-8+6-7+84+4+01)^5 \\ &:= (3-4+8-6+7+8-4-4+01)^{10} &:= (3-4-8-6+7+84+4+01)^5 \\ &:= (-3+4+8-6+7-8+4-4+01)^{20} &:= (-3-4-8-6-7-8+44+01)^{10} \\ &:= (3+4+8-6+7-8+4-4+01)^{10} &:= (3+4+8+6+7+8+44+01)^5 \\ &:= (3-4+8-6-7+8+4-4+01)^{20} &:= (-3+4-8-6-7-8-4+40+1)^{10} \\ &:= (-3-4+8+6-7+8+4-4+01)^{10} &:= (-3-4-8-6-7-8+4+40+1)^{10} \\ &:= (-3+4-8-6+7+8+4-4+01)^{20} &:= (3+4+8+6+7+8+4+40+1)^5 \\ &:= (3+4-8-6+7+8+4-4+01)^{10} &:= (-3-48+67-8+4-4+01)^{10} \\ &:= (-3+4+8-6+7-8-4+4+01)^{20} &:= (-3-48+67-8-4+4+01)^{10} \\ &:= (3+4+8-6+7-8-4+4+01)^{10} &:= (-3+48-6+7+8-44-01)^{10} \\ &:= (3-4+8-6-7+8-4+4+01)^{20} &:= (-3+48-6+7-8+44-01)^5 \\ &:= (-3-4+8+6-7+8-4+4+01)^{10} &:= (3-48+6+7-8+44-01)^{20} \\ &:= (-3+4-8-6+7+8-4+4+01)^{20} &:= (3+48-6-7+8-44+01)^{20} \\ &:= (3+4-8-6+7+8-4+4+01)^{10} &:= (-3+48+6-7+8-44+01)^{10} \\ &:= (3+4+8-6-7-8+4+4+01)^{20} &:= (-3+48+6-7-8+44+01)^5 \\ &:= (-3+4+8+6-7-8+4+4+01)^{10} &:= (-3-48-6+7+8+44+01)^{20} \\ &:= (-3-4+8-6+7-8+4+4+01)^{20} &:= (3-48-6+7+8+44+01)^{10} \\ &:= (3-4+8-6+7-8+4+4+01)^{10} &:= (-3+48-6+7+8-4-40-1)^{10} \\ &:= (3+4-8-6-7+8+4+4+01)^{20} &:= (-3+48-6-7+8+4-40-1)^{20} \\ &:= (-3+4-8+6-7+8+4+4+01)^{10} &:= (3+48-6-7+8+4-40-1)^{10} \\ &:= (-3-4-8-6+7+8+4+4+01)^{20} &:= (3+48-6-7+8-4+40-1)^5 \\ &:= (3-4-8-6+7+8+4+4+01)^{10} &:= (-3+48-6+7-8+4+40-1)^5 \\ &:= (3+48+6+7+8+4+4+01)^5 &:= (3-48+6+7-8+4+40-1)^{20} \\ &:= (-3+4+86-7+8-4-4+01)^5 &:= (3+48-6-7+8-4-40+1)^{20} \\ &:= (-3-4+86-7+8+4-4+01)^5 &:= (-3+48+6-7+8-4-40+1)^{10} \\ &:= (-3-4+86-7+8-4+4+01)^5 &:= (-3+48-6+7-8+4-40+1)^{20} \\ &:= (-3+4+86-7-8+4+4+01)^5 &:= (3+48-6+7-8+4-40+1)^{10} \\ &:= (3+4+8+67+8-4-4-01)^5 &:= (3+48-6+7-8-4+40+1)^5 \\ &:= (3-4+8+67+8+4-4-01)^5 &:= (-3+48+6-7-8+4+40+1)^5 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 &:= (-3 - 48 - 6 + 7 + 8 + 4 + 40 + 1)^{20} \\
 &:= (3 - 48 - 6 + 7 + 8 + 4 + 40 + 1)^{10} \\
 &:= (3 - 4 + 86 + 7 - 84 - 4 - 01)^{20} \\
 &:= (-3 + 4 - 86 + 7 + 84 + 4 - 01)^{10} \\
 &:= (-3 + 4 - 86 + 7 + 84 - 4 + 01)^{20} \\
 &:= (3 + 4 - 86 + 7 + 84 - 4 + 01)^{10} \\
 &:= (3 + 4 - 86 - 7 + 84 + 4 + 01)^{20} \\
 &:= (-3 - 4 - 86 + 7 + 84 + 4 + 01)^{20} \\
 &:= (3 - 4 - 86 + 7 + 84 + 4 + 01)^{10} \\
 &:= (3 - 4 - 8 - 67 + 84 - 4 - 01)^{20} \\
 &:= (3 + 4 + 8 + 67 - 84 + 4 + 01)^{20} \\
 &:= (-3 + 4 - 8 + 67 - 8 - 44 + 01)^{10} \\
 &:= (-3 + 4 - 8 + 67 - 8 - 4 - 40 + 1)^{10} \\
 &:= (-3 - 4 - 8 + 67 - 8 + 4 - 40 + 1)^{10} \\
 &:= (-3 - 4 - 8 + 67 - 8 - 4 + 40 + 1)^5 \\
 &:= (34 + 8 + 6 + 78 - 44 - 01)^5 \\
 &:= (-34 + 8 - 6 + 78 - 44 + 01)^{20} \\
 &:= (34 + 8 - 6 - 78 + 44 + 01)^{20} \\
 &:= (34 + 8 + 6 + 78 - 4 - 40 - 1)^5 \\
 &:= (-34 + 8 - 6 + 78 + 4 - 40 - 1)^{10} \\
 &:= (-34 + 8 - 6 + 78 - 4 + 40 - 1)^5 \\
 &:= (-34 + 8 - 6 + 78 - 4 - 40 + 1)^{20} \\
 &:= (34 + 8 - 6 - 78 + 4 + 40 + 1)^{20} \\
 &:= (3 + 48 + 67 + 8 - 44 - 01)^5 \\
 &:= (3 + 48 + 67 + 8 - 4 - 40 - 1)^5 \\
 &:= (3 + 48 - 6 - 7 + 84 - 40 - 1)^5 \\
 &:= (-3 + 48 - 6 + 7 - 84 + 40 + 1)^{20} \\
 &:= (3 + 48 - 6 + 7 - 84 + 40 + 1)^{10} \\
 &:= (3 - 48 - 6 + 7 + 84 + 40 + 1)^5 \\
 &:= (-3 - 4 - 8 + 67 - 84 + 40 + 1)^{10} \\
 &:= (-34 - 86 + 78 + 44 + 01)^{20} \\
 &:= (34 + 86 + 78 + 44 + 01)^4 \\
 &:= (-34 + 86 - 78 - 4 + 40 - 1)^{10} \\
 &:= (-34 - 86 + 78 + 4 + 40 + 1)^{20} \\
 &:= (34 + 86 + 78 + 4 + 40 + 1)^4 \\
 &:= (3 + 48 + 67 + 84 + 40 + 1)^4 \\
 &:= (-3 + 4 - 8 - 67 - 84 + 401)^4 \\
 &:= (-348 - 6 - 78 + 440 + 1)^{10}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 &:= (-34 - 86 - 78 + 440 + 1)^4 \\
 &:= (-3 - 486 + 7 + 84 + 401)^{20} \\
 &:= (3 - 486 + 7 + 84 + 401)^{10} \\
 \mathbf{3514592656} &:= (3 + 5 + 1 + 4 + 59265 + 6)^2 \\
 \mathbf{3518743761} &:= (3 + 5 + 1 + 8 + 7 + 4 - 3 + 7 + 6 + 1)^6 \\
 &:= (-3 + 5 + 1 + 8 + 7 + 4 + 3 + 7 + 6 + 1)^6 \\
 &:= (3 + 5 + 1 + 8 - 7 + 43 - 7 - 6 - 1)^6 \\
 &:= (3 - 5 - 1 - 8 + 7 + 43 + 7 - 6 - 1)^6 \\
 &:= (3 - 5 - 1 + 8 - 7 + 43 - 7 + 6 - 1)^6 \\
 &:= (3 - 5 + 1 - 8 + 7 + 43 - 7 + 6 - 1)^6 \\
 &:= (3 - 5 + 1 - 8 - 7 + 43 + 7 + 6 - 1)^6 \\
 &:= (3 + 5 - 1 + 8 - 7 + 43 - 7 - 6 + 1)^6 \\
 &:= (3 + 5 + 1 - 8 + 7 + 43 - 7 - 6 + 1)^6 \\
 &:= (-3 - 5 + 1 + 8 + 7 + 43 - 7 - 6 + 1)^6 \\
 &:= (3 + 5 + 1 - 8 - 7 + 43 + 7 - 6 + 1)^6 \\
 &:= (-3 - 5 + 1 + 8 - 7 + 43 + 7 - 6 + 1)^6 \\
 &:= (3 - 5 - 1 - 8 + 7 + 43 - 7 + 6 + 1)^6 \\
 &:= (3 - 5 - 1 - 8 - 7 + 43 + 7 + 6 + 1)^6 \\
 &:= (3 + 5 - 1 - 8 - 7 - 4 - 3 - 7 + 61)^6 \\
 &:= (-3 - 5 - 1 + 8 - 7 - 4 - 3 - 7 + 61)^6 \\
 &:= (-3 - 5 + 1 - 8 + 7 - 4 - 3 - 7 + 61)^6 \\
 &:= (3 - 5 + 1 - 8 - 7 + 4 - 3 - 7 + 61)^6 \\
 &:= (-3 + 5 - 1 - 8 - 7 - 4 + 3 - 7 + 61)^6 \\
 &:= (-3 - 5 + 1 - 8 - 7 + 4 + 3 - 7 + 61)^6 \\
 &:= (-3 - 5 + 1 - 8 - 7 - 4 - 3 + 7 + 61)^6 \\
 &:= (35 + 18 + 7 - 4 - 3 - 7 - 6 - 1)^6 \\
 &:= (35 + 18 - 7 + 4 + 3 - 7 - 6 - 1)^6 \\
 &:= (35 + 18 - 7 - 4 - 3 + 7 - 6 - 1)^6 \\
 &:= (35 + 18 - 7 - 4 - 3 - 7 + 6 + 1)^6 \\
 &:= (35 - 18 + 7 + 4 - 3 + 7 + 6 + 1)^6 \\
 &:= (-35 - 1 - 8 + 74 - 3 + 7 + 6 - 1)^6 \\
 &:= (-35 + 1 + 8 + 74 + 3 - 7 - 6 + 1)^6 \\
 &:= (-35 - 1 - 8 + 7 + 4 - 3 + 76 - 1)^6 \\
 &:= (-35 - 1 + 8 - 7 - 4 + 3 + 76 - 1)^6 \\
 &:= (-35 + 1 - 8 + 7 - 4 + 3 + 76 - 1)^6 \\
 &:= (-35 - 1 - 8 + 7 - 4 + 3 + 76 + 1)^6 \\
 &:= (3 - 51 + 8 + 74 + 3 + 7 - 6 + 1)^6 \\
 &:= (-3 - 51 + 8 + 74 - 3 + 7 + 6 + 1)^6
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 & := (-3 - 51 + 8 + 7 + 4 - 3 + 76 + 1)^6 & := (3 + 544 - 5 + 3 - 5 - 296)^4 \\
 & := (3 - 5 - 18 + 74 - 3 - 7 - 6 + 1)^6 & := (-3 - 54 + 45 + 352 - 96)^4 \\
 & := (-3 - 5 - 18 + 74 + 3 - 7 - 6 + 1)^6 & \mathbf{3546578125} := (-3 + 54 + 657 + 812 + 5)^3 \\
 & := (-3 + 5 + 18 - 7 - 4 + 37 - 6 - 1)^6 & \mathbf{3553559576} := (35 + 535 + 5 + 957 - 6)^3 \\
 & := (-3 - 5 + 18 - 7 + 4 + 37 - 6 + 1)^6 & \mathbf{3559673569} := (3 - 5 + 59673 - 5 + 6 - 9)^2 \\
 & := (-3 + 5 - 18 + 7 + 4 + 37 + 6 + 1)^6 & := (-3 - 5 + 59673 - 5 - 6 + 9)^2 \\
 & := (3 + 5 + 1 + 87 - 43 - 7 - 6 - 1)^6 & \mathbf{3566597841} := (-3 + 5 - 66 + 59784 + 1)^2 \\
 & := (3 - 5 - 1 + 87 - 43 - 7 + 6 - 1)^6 & \mathbf{3574558889} := (3 + 574 + 55 + 888 + 9)^3 \\
 & := (3 + 5 - 1 + 87 - 43 - 7 - 6 + 1)^6 & := (3 + 574 + 55 + 8 + 889)^3 \\
 & := (-3 - 5 + 1 + 87 - 43 + 7 - 6 + 1)^6 & := (3 + 574 + 5 + 58 + 889)^3 \\
 & := (3 + 5 - 1 + 87 - 4 + 3 + 7 - 61)^6 & := (3 + 5 + 74 + 558 + 889)^3 \\
 & := (3 - 5 + 1 + 87 + 4 + 3 + 7 - 61)^6 & \mathbf{3581577000} := (3 + 5 + 815 + 7 + 700 + 0)^3 \\
 & := (-3 + 5 - 1 + 8 + 74 - 37 - 6 - 1)^6 & \mathbf{3600360009} := (3 - 6 - 003 + 60009)^2 \\
 & := (3 - 5 + 1 + 8 + 74 - 37 - 6 + 1)^6 & := (-3 - 6 + 003 + 60009)^2 \\
 & := (-3 + 5 + 1 - 8 + 74 - 37 + 6 + 1)^6 & \mathbf{3603000625} := (-36 + 0300 + 06 - 25)^4 \\
 & := (3 - 5 + 1 + 8 + 7 - 43 + 7 + 61)^6 & \mathbf{3603600900} := (3 - 60 - 3 + 60090 + 0)^2 \\
 & := (35 - 18 - 7 + 43 - 7 - 6 - 1)^6 & := (-3 - 60 + 3 + 60090 + 0)^2 \\
 & := (35 + 1 + 87 - 4 - 3 - 76 - 1)^6 & \mathbf{3616805375} := (361 - 6 + 805 + 375)^3 \\
 & := (35 - 1 + 87 - 4 - 3 - 76 + 1)^6 & \mathbf{3623878656} := (-3 + 6 + 2 - 3 + 878 + 656)^3 \\
 & := (35 - 1 + 8 - 74 + 3 + 7 + 61)^6 & := (3 - 6 + 2 + 3 + 878 + 656)^3 \\
 & := (35 - 1 - 8 - 7 - 4 - 37 + 61)^6 & \mathbf{3645153819} := (-3 - 6 - 4 - 5 + 1538 + 19)^3 \\
 & := (-3 + 51 - 87 + 4 - 3 + 76 + 1)^6 & := (-36 + 45 + 1538 + 1 - 9)^3 \\
 & := (3 + 51 + 8 - 74 - 3 - 7 + 61)^6 & := (36 - 45 + 1538 + 1 + 9)^3 \\
 & := (-3 + 51 + 8 - 74 + 3 - 7 + 61)^6 & \mathbf{3651059776} := (-3 + 651 + 059776)^2 \\
 & := (-3 - 51 - 8 + 7 - 4 + 37 + 61)^6 & \mathbf{3662186256} := (-3 + 6 + 6 + 218 + 6 + 2 + 5 + 6)^4 \\
 & := (3 - 51 - 8 - 7 + 4 + 37 + 61)^6 & := (3 + 6 - 6 + 2 - 1 - 8 - 6 + 256)^4 \\
 & := (3 - 5 + 18 + 74 + 3 + 7 - 61)^6 & := (3 - 6 + 6 + 2 - 1 - 8 - 6 + 256)^4 \\
 & := (3 + 5 + 18 - 7 - 4 - 37 + 61)^6 & := (3 - 6 - 6 - 2 - 1 + 8 - 6 + 256)^4 \\
 & := (3 - 5 - 1 - 8 + 74 + 37 - 61)^6 & := (-3 - 6 - 6 + 2 + 1 + 8 - 6 + 256)^4 \\
 & := (3 + 5 - 1 + 8 - 74 + 37 + 61)^6 & := (3 - 6 - 6 + 2 - 1 - 8 + 6 + 256)^4 \\
 & := (3 + 51 + 87 - 4 - 37 - 61)^6 & := (-3 + 66 - 2 + 186 - 2 - 5 + 6)^4 \\
 & := (3 + 5 + 1 + 8 + 743 + 761)^3 & := (3 - 6 + 62 + 186 + 2 + 5 - 6)^4 \\
 & := (35 - 18 + 743 + 761)^3 & := (3 + 6 + 6 + 218 - 6 + 25 - 6)^4 \\
 \mathbf{3524559424} & := (-3 - 52 + 4 - 5 + 59424)^2 & := (3 + 6 - 6 + 218 + 6 + 25 - 6)^4 \\
 \mathbf{3544535296} & := (3 - 54 - 4 + 5 + 3 - 5 + 296)^4 & := (3 - 6 + 6 + 218 + 6 + 25 - 6)^4 \\
 & := (3 - 54 - 4 - 5 + 3 + 5 + 296)^4 & := (3 + 6 - 6 + 218 - 6 + 25 + 6)^4 \\
 & := (3 - 5 + 4 + 4 - 53 - 5 + 296)^4 & := (3 - 6 + 6 + 218 - 6 + 25 + 6)^4 \\
 & := (35 + 4 + 4 + 53 + 52 + 96)^4 & := (3 - 6 - 6 + 218 + 6 + 25 + 6)^4
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 & := (-3 + 6 + 6 - 21 + 8 - 6 + 256)^4 \\
 & := (-3 + 6 - 6 - 21 + 8 + 6 + 256)^4 \\
 & := (-3 - 6 + 6 - 21 + 8 + 6 + 256)^4 \\
 & := (366 - 21 - 86 - 2 - 5 - 6)^4 \\
 & := (366 - 2 - 1 - 86 - 25 - 6)^4 \\
 & := (-366 + 2 - 1 - 8 + 625 - 6)^4 \\
 \mathbf{3666512088} & := (-3666 + 5120 + 88)^3 \\
 \mathbf{3707398432} & := (-3 + 7 - 07 - 3 + 9 + 84 - 3 - 2)^5 \\
 & := (-3 - 7 + 07 - 3 + 9 + 84 - 3 - 2)^5 \\
 & := (3 + 7 - 07 + 3 - 9 + 84 + 3 - 2)^5 \\
 & := (3 - 7 + 07 + 3 - 9 + 84 + 3 - 2)^5 \\
 & := (-3 + 7 + 07 - 3 - 9 + 84 - 3 + 2)^5 \\
 & := (3 + 7 + 07 + 3 + 9 + 8 + 43 + 2)^5 \\
 & := (37 + 07 + 39 + 8 - 4 - 3 - 2)^5 \\
 & := (37 - 07 + 39 + 8 + 4 + 3 - 2)^5 \\
 & := (37 + 07 + 3 - 9 + 8 + 4 + 32)^5 \\
 & := (-3 + 70 - 7 + 39 - 8 - 4 - 3 - 2)^5 \\
 & := (-3 + 70 + 7 - 3 - 9 - 8 - 4 + 32)^5 \\
 & := (3 + 70 - 7 - 3 - 9 - 8 + 4 + 32)^5 \\
 & := (-3 + 70 - 7 + 3 - 9 - 8 + 4 + 32)^5 \\
 & := (-3 - 7 + 073 - 9 - 8 + 4 + 32)^5 \\
 & := (3 + 7 + 07 + 3 + 98 - 4 - 32)^5 \\
 & := (37 + 073 + 9 + 8 - 43 - 2)^5 \\
 & := (-37 + 073 + 9 - 8 + 43 + 2)^5 \\
 & := (-3 + 70 - 73 + 9 + 84 - 3 - 2)^5 \\
 & := (3 - 70 + 73 - 9 + 84 + 3 - 2)^5 \\
 & := (-3 + 70 + 73 - 9 - 8 - 43 + 2)^5 \\
 & := (3 + 70 + 7 + 39 + 8 - 43 - 2)^5 \\
 & := (3 - 70 + 7 + 3 + 98 + 43 - 2)^5 \\
 \mathbf{3722098081} & := (37 + 220 - 9 + 8 - 08 - 1)^4 \\
 & := (37 + 220 - 9 - 8 + 08 - 1)^4 \\
 & := (37 + 2 + 209 + 8 - 08 - 1)^4 \\
 & := (37 + 2 + 209 - 8 + 08 - 1)^4 \\
 & := (3 + 72 + 2 + 09 + 80 + 81)^4 \\
 & := (372 - 20 - 98 - 08 + 1)^4 \\
 & := (-37 + 220 - 9 + 80 - 8 + 1)^4 \\
 & := (-37 + 220 - 9 - 8 + 081)^4 \\
 & := (-37 + 2 + 209 + 80 - 8 + 1)^4 \\
 & := (-37 + 2 + 209 - 8 + 081)^4 \\
 & := (3 + 72 + 20 - 9 + 80 + 81)^4 \\
 & := (3 + 7 + 220 + 98 - 081)^4 \\
 & := (37 + 220 - 9 + 80 - 81)^4 \\
 & := (37 + 2 + 209 + 80 - 81)^4 \\
 \mathbf{3752779464} & := (3 + 752 + 7 + 794 - 6 + 4)^3 \\
 \mathbf{3759161344} & := (-37 - 5 + 9 + 1 + 61344)^2 \\
 \mathbf{3767287616} & := (-3 + 76 + 728 + 761 - 6)^3 \\
 \mathbf{3782742016} & := (-37 + 8 + 274 - 2 - 01 + 6)^4 \\
 & := (3 - 7 - 8 + 274 + 2 - 016)^4 \\
 & := (3 + 7 + 8 + 27 - 4 + 201 + 6)^4 \\
 \mathbf{3796161769} & := (-3 - 7 + 9 + 61617 + 6 - 9)^2 \\
 & := (-3 - 7 - 9 + 61617 + 6 + 9)^2 \\
 \mathbf{3803721481} & := (3 + 8 - 03 + 72 + 1481)^3 \\
 & := (-3 + 8 + 03 + 72 + 1481)^3 \\
 \mathbf{3825694144} & := (-3 - 8 - 2569 + 4144)^3 \\
 \mathbf{3844124001} & := (3 + 8 + 4 - 4 - 1 + 240 - 01)^4 \\
 & := (3 + 8 - 4 + 4 - 1 + 240 - 01)^4 \\
 \mathbf{3855122432} & := (3 - 855 - 12 + 2432)^3 \\
 \mathbf{3862125316} & := (3 + 8 + 62125 + 3 + 1 + 6)^2 \\
 \mathbf{3862622500} & := (-38 - 62 + 62250 + 0)^2 \\
 \mathbf{3884701248} & := (-3 + 884 + 701 + 2 - 4 - 8)^3 \\
 & := (3 + 884 + 701 - 24 + 8)^3 \\
 \mathbf{3892119517} & := (-38 + 9 + 2119 - 517)^3 \\
 \mathbf{3899547224} & := (3 + 899 - 54 + 722 + 4)^3 \\
 & := (389 + 954 + 7 + 224)^3 \\
 \mathbf{3906250000} & := (-3 + 9 - 06 + 250 + 000)^4 \\
 & := (3 - 9 + 06 + 250 + 000)^4 \\
 \mathbf{3906625009} & := (-3 + 9 + 06 + 62500 - 9)^2 \\
 & := (-3 - 9 + 06 + 62500 + 9)^2 \\
 \mathbf{3929352552} & := (-3 + 92 + 935 + 2 + 552)^3 \\
 \mathbf{3939040643} & := (3 + 9 - 3 + 9 + 04 + 064 - 3)^5 \\
 & := (-3 + 9 + 3 + 9 + 04 + 064 - 3)^5 \\
 & := (-3 + 9 - 3 + 9 + 04 + 064 + 3)^5 \\
 & := (39 + 39 + 04 - 06 + 4 + 3)^5 \\
 & := (3 - 9 - 3 - 9 + 040 + 64 - 3)^5 \\
 & := (-3 - 9 + 3 - 9 + 040 + 64 - 3)^5 \\
 & := (-3 - 9 - 3 - 9 + 040 + 64 + 3)^5
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 &:= (3+9+3-9+040-6+43)^5 \\
 &:= (3-9+3+9+040-6+43)^5 \\
 &:= (-3+9-3-9+040+6+43)^5 \\
 &:= (-3-9-3+9+040+6+43)^5 \\
 &:= (-39-3+90+40-6+4-3)^5 \\
 &:= (3+93-90+40-6+43)^5 \\
 &:= (-3-93+90+40+6+43)^5 \\
 \mathbf{3969126001} &:= (-3+9-6-9+1+260-01)^4 \\
 &:= (3-9+6-9+1+260-01)^4 \\
 &:= (-3-9-6+9+1+260-01)^4 \\
 &:= (-3+9-6-9-1+260+01)^4 \\
 &:= (3-9+6-9-1+260+01)^4 \\
 &:= (-3-9-6+9-1+260+01)^4 \\
 &:= (3+96+91+2+60-01)^4 \\
 &:= (-3-96+91+260-01)^4 \\
 \mathbf{3981876625} &:= (3-9+818+766+2+5)^3 \\
 \mathbf{4012099469} &:= (-40-1+2099-469)^3 \\
 \mathbf{4032758016} &:= (4-03+275-8-016)^4 \\
 &:= (4-0327+580+1-6)^4 \\
 \mathbf{4034866688} &:= (4+034+866+688)^3 \\
 \mathbf{4097152081} &:= (40+9-7-1+5+208-1)^4 \\
 &:= (40-9+7+1+5+208+1)^4 \\
 &:= (4+09+7+152+081)^4 \\
 &:= (40+9+71+52+081)^4 \\
 &:= (40+97+15+20+81)^4 \\
 \mathbf{4111379208} &:= (4+11+1379+208)^3 \\
 \mathbf{4125364441} &:= (41-253+64441)^2 \\
 \mathbf{4134520125} &:= (-413-4+5+2012+5)^3 \\
 \mathbf{4139764281} &:= (41+3+9+7+64281)^2 \\
 \mathbf{4162314256} &:= (4+16+231+4-2-5+6)^4 \\
 &:= (4-16+2+3+1+4+256)^4 \\
 &:= (4+1-62+314-2+5-6)^4 \\
 &:= (4-1-62+314-2-5+6)^4 \\
 &:= (4+1+6-2+3-14+256)^4 \\
 &:= (-4-1-6-2-3+14+256)^4 \\
 &:= (-41+6+231+4-2+56)^4 \\
 &:= (41-6-2-31-4+256)^4 \\
 &:= (-41+6-2+31+4+256)^4
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 &:= (-4+162-3+1+42+56)^4 \\
 &:= (-4-16+231+42-5+6)^4 \\
 &:= (4-16+231+4+25+6)^4 \\
 &:= (-4-16+23-1-4+256)^4 \\
 &:= (-4+1+62-3+142+56)^4 \\
 &:= (4-1+6+231-42+56)^4 \\
 &:= (-4-1-6+23-14+256)^4 \\
 &:= (41-6-23-14+256)^4 \\
 \mathbf{4167864481} &:= (4-1+67+8+64481)^2 \\
 \mathbf{4181062131} &:= (418+1062+131)^3 \\
 \mathbf{4182119424} &:= (4+1+82-1-1+9-4-2-4)^5 \\
 &:= (4-1+82+1-1+9-4-2-4)^5 \\
 &:= (4-1+82-1+1+9-4-2-4)^5 \\
 &:= (-4+1+82-1-1+9+4-2-4)^5 \\
 &:= (-4-1+82+1-1+9+4-2-4)^5 \\
 &:= (-4-1+82-1+1+9+4-2-4)^5 \\
 &:= (-4+1+82+1+1+9-4+2-4)^5 \\
 &:= (-4+1+82-1-1+9-4-2+4)^5 \\
 &:= (-4-1+82+1-1+9-4-2+4)^5 \\
 &:= (-4-1+82-1+1+9-4-2+4)^5 \\
 &:= (4+1+82+1-1-9+4-2+4)^5 \\
 &:= (4+1+82-1+1-9+4-2+4)^5 \\
 &:= (4-1+82+1+1-9+4-2+4)^5 \\
 &:= (4-1+82-1-1-9+4+2+4)^5 \\
 &:= (41+8+21-1+9+4-2+4)^5 \\
 &:= (41-8+2+1+1+9+42-4)^5 \\
 &:= (41+8-2+1-1-9+42+4)^5 \\
 &:= (41+8-2-1+1-9+42+4)^5 \\
 &:= (41-8-2-1-1+9+42+4)^5 \\
 &:= (41+8-2+1-1+9+4+24)^5 \\
 &:= (41+8-2-1+1+9+4+24)^5 \\
 &:= (4-18+2+1-1+94-2+4)^5 \\
 &:= (4-18+2-1+1+94-2+4)^5 \\
 &:= (4-18-2+1-1+94+2+4)^5 \\
 &:= (4-18-2-1+1+94+2+4)^5 \\
 &:= (-4+1+8+2-11+94-2-4)^5 \\
 &:= (-4-1-8-2+11+94-2-4)^5 \\
 &:= (-4+1+8-2-11+94+2-4)^5
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 &:= (4 + 1 - 8 + 2 - 11 + 94 - 2 + 4)^5 & &:= (42 + 282 - 50 + 6 - 25)^4 \\
 &:= (4 + 1 - 8 - 2 - 11 + 94 + 2 + 4)^5 & &:= (-42 + 28 + 250 - 6 + 25)^4 \\
 &:= (41 + 82 - 1 - 1 + 9 - 42 - 4)^5 & &:= (4 - 228 - 2 + 506 - 25)^4 \\
 &:= (41 + 82 - 1 - 1 - 9 - 4 - 24)^5 & &:= (4 + 2 - 282 + 506 + 25)^4 \\
 &:= (41 - 8 + 21 + 1 - 9 + 42 - 4)^5 & & \mathbf{4256518564} := (42 + 5 + 65185 + 6 + 4)^2 \\
 &:= (41 + 8 - 21 + 1 + 9 + 42 + 4)^5 & & &:= (-4 + 2 - 5 + 65185 + 64)^2 \\
 &:= (41 - 8 + 21 + 1 + 9 - 4 + 24)^5 & & \mathbf{4262653521} := (-4 + 2 - 62 + 65352 + 1)^2 \\
 &:= (4 + 182 - 1 - 1 - 94 - 2 - 4)^5 & & \mathbf{4267293848} := (42 + 6 + 729 - 3 + 848)^3 \\
 &:= (-4 + 182 + 1 + 1 - 94 + 2 - 4)^5 & & \mathbf{4275191367} := (-42 + 751 + 913 - 6 + 7)^3 \\
 &:= (-4 + 182 - 1 - 1 - 94 - 2 + 4)^5 & & \mathbf{4291015625} := (-4 - 2 - 9 + 1015 + 625)^3 \\
 &:= (-4 + 18 - 21 - 1 + 94 + 2 - 4)^5 & & \mathbf{4293656676} := (-42 - 93 + 65667 - 6)^2 \\
 &:= (4 + 18 - 2 - 1 + 19 + 42 + 4)^5 & & \mathbf{4294967296} := (4 + 2 + 9 - 4 + 9 + 6 - 7 - 2 - 9 - 6)^{32} \\
 &:= (-4 + 18 + 2 - 1 - 1 + 94 - 24)^5 & & &:= (-4 + 2 + 9 + 4 + 9 + 6 - 7 - 2 - 9 - 6)^{32} \\
 &:= (-4 + 18 - 2 + 1 + 1 + 94 - 24)^5 & & &:= (4 + 2 + 9 - 4 + 9 - 6 + 7 - 2 - 9 - 6)^{16} \\
 &:= (4 + 1 + 8 - 2 + 119 - 42 - 4)^5 & & &:= (-4 + 2 + 9 + 4 + 9 - 6 + 7 - 2 - 9 - 6)^{16} \\
 &:= (-4 + 1 + 8 - 2 + 119 - 42 + 4)^5 & & &:= (4 - 2 + 9 + 4 - 9 + 6 + 7 - 2 - 9 - 6)^{32} \\
 &:= (4 - 1 - 8 - 2 + 119 - 4 - 24)^5 & & &:= (-4 - 2 + 9 - 4 + 9 + 6 + 7 - 2 - 9 - 6)^{16} \\
 &:= (-4 - 1 - 8 - 2 + 119 + 4 - 24)^5 & & &:= (4 + 2 + 9 - 4 + 9 + 6 + 7 - 2 - 9 - 6)^8 \\
 &:= (-4 + 1 + 8 - 2 + 11 + 94 - 24)^5 & & &:= (4 - 2 - 9 + 4 + 9 + 6 + 7 - 2 - 9 - 6)^{32} \\
 &:= (41 - 82 + 119 + 4 - 2 + 4)^5 & & &:= (-4 + 2 + 9 + 4 + 9 + 6 + 7 - 2 - 9 - 6)^8 \\
 &:= (4 - 18 - 21 + 1 + 94 + 24)^5 & & &:= (4 + 2 + 9 + 4 + 9 - 6 - 7 + 2 - 9 - 6)^{32} \\
 &:= (-4 + 1 - 82 - 1 + 194 - 24)^5 & & &:= (4 - 2 + 9 - 4 + 9 + 6 - 7 + 2 - 9 - 6)^{32} \\
 &:= (-4 - 1 - 82 + 1 + 194 - 24)^5 & & &:= (-4 - 2 + 9 + 4 + 9 + 6 - 7 + 2 - 9 - 6)^{32} \\
 \mathbf{4227952113} &:= (-422 - 79 + 5 + 2113)^3 & & &:= (4 - 2 + 9 - 4 + 9 - 6 + 7 + 2 - 9 - 6)^{16} \\
 \mathbf{4228250625} &:= (4 - 2 - 2 + 8 + 250 - 6 - 2 + 5)^4 & & &:= (-4 - 2 + 9 + 4 + 9 - 6 + 7 + 2 - 9 - 6)^{16} \\
 &:= (-4 + 2 + 2 + 8 + 250 - 6 - 2 + 5)^4 & & &:= (4 + 2 + 9 + 4 + 9 - 6 + 7 + 2 - 9 - 6)^8 \\
 &:= (4 + 2 - 2 - 8 + 250 + 6 - 2 + 5)^4 & & &:= (4 + 2 + 9 - 4 - 9 + 6 + 7 + 2 - 9 - 6)^{32} \\
 &:= (4 - 2 + 2 - 8 + 250 + 6 - 2 + 5)^4 & & &:= (-4 + 2 + 9 + 4 - 9 + 6 + 7 + 2 - 9 - 6)^{32} \\
 &:= (-4 + 2 - 2 + 8 + 250 - 6 + 2 + 5)^4 & & &:= (4 + 2 - 9 - 4 + 9 + 6 + 7 + 2 - 9 - 6)^{32} \\
 &:= (-4 - 2 + 2 + 8 + 250 - 6 + 2 + 5)^4 & & &:= (4 - 2 + 9 - 4 + 9 + 6 + 7 + 2 - 9 - 6)^8 \\
 &:= (4 - 2 - 2 - 8 + 250 + 6 + 2 + 5)^4 & & &:= (-4 + 2 - 9 + 4 + 9 + 6 + 7 + 2 - 9 - 6)^{32} \\
 &:= (-4 + 2 + 2 - 8 + 250 + 6 + 2 + 5)^4 & & &:= (-4 - 2 + 9 + 4 + 9 + 6 + 7 + 2 - 9 - 6)^8 \\
 &:= (4 + 22 - 8 + 250 - 6 - 2 - 5)^4 & & &:= (4 - 2 + 9 - 4 + 9 - 6 - 7 - 2 + 9 - 6)^{16} \\
 &:= (42 - 28 + 250 - 6 + 2 - 5)^4 & & &:= (-4 - 2 + 9 + 4 + 9 - 6 - 7 - 2 + 9 - 6)^{16} \\
 &:= (-42 - 2 - 8 + 250 + 62 - 5)^4 & & &:= (4 + 2 + 9 + 4 + 9 - 6 - 7 - 2 + 9 - 6)^8 \\
 &:= (42 + 2 - 8 + 250 - 6 - 25)^4 & & &:= (4 + 2 + 9 - 4 - 9 + 6 - 7 - 2 + 9 - 6)^{32} \\
 &:= (4 - 22 - 8 + 250 + 6 + 25)^4 & & &:= (-4 + 2 + 9 + 4 - 9 + 6 - 7 - 2 + 9 - 6)^{32} \\
 &:= (4 - 2 - 28 + 250 + 6 + 25)^4 & & &:= (4 + 2 - 9 - 4 + 9 + 6 - 7 - 2 + 9 - 6)^{32}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} & := (4-2+9-4+9+6-7-2+9-6)^8 \\ & := (-4+2-9+4+9+6-7-2+9-6)^{32} \\ & := (-4-2+9+4+9+6-7-2+9-6)^8 \\ & := (4+2+9-4-9-6+7-2+9-6)^{16} \\ & := (-4+2+9+4-9-6+7-2+9-6)^{16} \\ & := (4+2-9-4+9-6+7-2+9-6)^{16} \\ & := (-4+2-9+4+9-6+7-2+9-6)^{16} \\ & := (-4-2+9-4-9+6+7-2+9-6)^{16} \\ & := (4+2+9-4-9+6+7-2+9-6)^8 \\ & := (4-2-9+4-9+6+7-2+9-6)^{32} \\ & := (-4+2+9+4-9+6+7-2+9-6)^8 \\ & := (-4-2-9-4+9+6+7-2+9-6)^{16} \\ & := (4+2-9-4+9+6+7-2+9-6)^8 \\ & := (-4+2-9+4+9+6+7-2+9-6)^8 \\ & := (4+2+9+4-9-6-7+2+9-6)^{32} \\ & := (-4+2+9-4+9-6-7+2+9-6)^{16} \\ & := (4+2-9+4+9-6-7+2+9-6)^{32} \\ & := (4-2+9+4+9-6-7+2+9-6)^8 \\ & := (4-2+9-4-9+6-7+2+9-6)^{32} \\ & := (-4-2+9+4-9+6-7+2+9-6)^{32} \\ & := (4-2-9-4+9+6-7+2+9-6)^{32} \\ & := (-4+2+9-4+9+6-7+2+9-6)^8 \\ & := (-4-2-9+4+9+6-7+2+9-6)^{32} \\ & := (4-2+9-4-9-6+7+2+9-6)^{16} \\ & := (-4-2+9+4-9-6+7+2+9-6)^{16} \\ & := (4+2+9+4-9-6+7+2+9-6)^8 \\ & := (4-2-9-4+9-6+7+2+9-6)^{16} \\ & := (-4-2-9+4+9-6+7+2+9-6)^{16} \\ & := (4+2-9+4+9-6+7+2+9-6)^8 \\ & := (4+2-9-4-9+6+7+2+9-6)^{32} \\ & := (4-2+9-4-9+6+7+2+9-6)^8 \\ & := (-4+2-9+4-9+6+7+2+9-6)^{32} \\ & := (-4-2-9-4+9+6-7-2+9+6)^{32} \\ & := (-4-2+9+4-9-6-7-2+9+6)^{16} \\ & := (4+2+9+4-9-6+7-2+9+6)^8 \\ & := (-4-2-9-4+9+6-7-2+9+6)^{32} \\ & := (-4-2+9+4-9-6+7-2+9+6)^{16} \\ & := (4+2+9-4-9-6+7-2+9+6)^8 \\ & := (4-2-9+4-9-6+7-2+9+6)^{32} \\ & := (-4+2+9+4-9-6+7-2+9+6)^8 \\ & := (-4-2-9-4+9-6+7-2+9+6)^{16} \\ & := (4+2-9-4+9-6+7-2+9+6)^8 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} & := (-4+2-9+4+9-6+7-2+9+6)^8 \\ & := (-4+2-9-4-9+6+7-2+9+6)^{32} \\ & := (-4-2+9-4-9+6+7-2+9+6)^8 \\ & := (-4-2-9-4+9+6+7-2+9+6)^8 \\ & := (4-2+9-4-9-6-7+2+9+6)^{32} \\ & := (-4-2+9+4-9-6-7+2+9+6)^{32} \\ & := (4-2-9-4+9-6-7+2+9+6)^{32} \\ & := (-4+2+9-4+9-6-7+2+9+6)^8 \\ & := (-4-2-9+4+9-6-7+2+9+6)^{32} \\ & := (4-2-9+4-9+6-7+2+9+6)^{16} \\ & := (4+2-9-4-9-6+7+2+9+6)^{32} \\ & := (4-2+9-4-9-6+7+2+9+6)^8 \\ & := (-4+2-9+4-9-6+7+2+9+6)^{32} \\ & := (-4-2+9+4-9-6+7+2+9+6)^8 \\ & := (4-2-9-4+9-6+7+2+9+6)^8 \\ & := (-4-2-9+4+9-6+7+2+9+6)^8 \\ & := (-4-2-9-4-9+6+7+2+9+6)^{32} \\ & := (42+9+4-9-6-7-2-9-6)^8 \\ & := (42-9+4+9-6-7-2-9-6)^8 \\ & := (42-9-4-9+6-7-2-9-6)^{32} \\ & := (42-9-4-9-6+7-2-9-6)^{16} \\ & := (42-9-4-9+6+7-2-9-6)^8 \\ & := (42-9+4-9-6-7+2-9-6)^{32} \\ & := (42-9+4-9-6+7+2-9-6)^8 \\ & := (42-9+4-9-6-7-2+9-6)^8 \\ & := (42-9-4-9-6-7-2-9+6)^{32} \\ & := (42-9-4-9-6+7-2-9+6)^8 \\ & := (-42+9-4+9+6+7+2+9+6)^{32} \\ & := (4+29+4+9-6-7-2-9-6)^8 \\ & := (4+29-4-9+6-7-2-9-6)^{32} \\ & := (-4+29+4-9+6-7-2-9-6)^{32} \\ & := (4+29-4-9-6+7-2-9-6)^{16} \\ & := (-4+29+4-9-6+7-2-9-6)^{16} \\ & := (4+29-4-9+6+7-2-9-6)^8 \\ & := (-4+29+4-9+6+7-2-9-6)^8 \\ & := (4+29+4-9-6-7+2-9-6)^{32} \\ & := (-4+29-4+9-6-7+2-9-6)^{16} \\ & := (-4+29-4+9+6-7+2-9-6)^8 \end{aligned}$$
$$\begin{aligned} & := (4+29+4-9-6+7+2-9-6)^8 \\ & := (4+29+4-9-6-7-2+9-6)^8 \\ & := (4-29+4+9+6+7-2+9-6)^{32} \\ & := (-4+29-4-9-6-7+2+9-6)^{16} \\ & := (-4+29-4-9+6-7+2+9-6)^8 \\ & := (4+29-4-9-6-7-2-9+6)^{32} \\ & := (-4+29+4-9-6-7-2-9+6)^{32} \\ & := (4+29-4-9-6+7-2-9+6)^8 \\ & := (-4+29+4-9-6+7-2-9+6)^8 \\ & := (-4+29-4+9-6-7+2-9+6)^8 \\ & := (4-29+4+9-6+7-2+9+6)^{32} \\ & := (-4+29-4-9-6-7+2+9+6)^8 \\ & := (4-29+4+9-6+7-2+9+6)^{32} \\ & := (-4+29-4-9-6-7+2+9+6)^8 \\ & := (4-29+4+9+6-7+2+9+6)^{16} \\ & := (-4-29-4+9+6+7+2+9+6)^{32} \\ & := (-4-2-9+49-6-7-2-9-6)^{16} \\ & := (4+2-9+49-6-7-2-9-6)^8 \\ & := (-4-2-9+49+6-7-2-9-6)^8 \\ & := (4-2-9+49-6-7+2-9-6)^8 \\ & := (-4-2-9+49-6-7-2-9+6)^8 \\ & := (4-2+9+4+9+6+7-29-6)^{32} \\ & := (-4+2+9-4-9-6-7+29-6)^{16} \\ & := (4+2-9+4-9-6-7+29-6)^{32} \\ & := (4-2+9+4-9-6-7+29-6)^8 \\ & := (-4+2-9-4+9-6-7+29-6)^{16} \\ & := (4-2-9+4+9-6-7+29-6)^8 \\ & := (4-2-9-4-9+6-7+29-6)^{32} \\ & := (-4+2+9-4-9+6-7+29-6)^8 \\ & := (-4-2-9+4-9+6-7+29-6)^{32} \\ & := (-4+2-9-4+9+6-7+29-6)^8 \\ & := (4-2-9-4-9-6+7+29-6)^{16} \\ & := (-4-2-9+4-9-6+7+29-6)^{16} \\ & := (4+2-9+4-9-6+7+29-6)^8 \\ & := (4-2-9-4-9+6+7+29-6)^8 \\ & := (-4-2-9+4-9+6+7+29-6)^8 \\ & := (4+2+9+4+9+6-7-29+6)^{16} \\ & := (4-2+9+4+9-6+7-29+6)^{32} \\ & := (-4+2+9-4+9+6+7-29+6)^{32} \\ & := (4-2-9-4-9-6-7+29+6)^{32} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} & := (-4+2+9-4-9-6-7+29+6)^8 & := (-42-9-4-9+67-2+9+6)^8 \\ & := (-4-2-9+4-9-6-7+29+6)^{32} & := (42+9+4+9-6-7-29-6)^8 \\ & := (-4+2-9-4+9-6-7+29+6)^8 & := (42+9-4-9+6-7-29-6)^{32} \\ & := (4-2-9-4-9-6+7+29+6)^8 & := (42-9-4+9+6-7-29-6)^{32} \\ & := (-4-2-9+4-9-6+7+29+6)^8 & := (42+9-4-9-6+7-29-6)^{16} \\ & := (-42+9+49+6-7+2-9-6)^{32} & := (42-9-4+9-6+7-29-6)^{16} \\ & := (-42+9+49-6+7+2-9-6)^{16} & := (42+9-4-9+6+7-29-6)^8 \\ & := (42+9-49+6+7+2-9-6)^{32} & := (42-9-4+9+6+7-29-6)^8 \\ & := (-42+9+49+6+7+2-9-6)^8 & := (-42+9+4+9+6-7+29-6)^{32} \\ & := (-42+9+49-6-7-2+9-6)^{16} & := (-42+9+4+9-6+7+29-6)^{16} \\ & := (42+9-49+6-7-2+9-6)^{32} & := (-42+9+4+9+6+7+29-6)^8 \\ & := (-42+9+49+6-7-2+9-6)^8 & := (42+9-4-9-6-7-29+6)^{32} \\ & := (42+9-49-6+7-2+9-6)^{16} & := (42-9-4+9-6-7-29+6)^{32} \\ & := (42+9-49+6+7-2+9-6)^8 & := (42-9+4-9+6-7-29+6)^{16} \\ & := (-42-9+49+6-7+2+9-6)^{32} & := (42+9-4-9-6+7-29+6)^8 \\ & := (-42-9+49-6+7+2+9-6)^{16} & := (42-9-4+9-6+7-29+6)^8 \\ & := (42-9-49+6+7+2+9-6)^{32} & := (-42+9+4+9-6-7+29+6)^{32} \\ & := (-42-9+49+6+7+2+9-6)^8 & := (-42+9+4+9-6+7+29+6)^8 \\ & := (-42+9+49-6-7+2-9+6)^{32} & := (-42+9-4-9+6+7+29+6)^{32} \\ & := (42+9-49-6+7+2-9+6)^{32} & := (-42-9-4+9+6+7+29+6)^{32} \\ & := (-42+9+49-6+7+2-9+6)^8 & := (-4-29+49+6-7+2-9-6)^{32} \\ & := (42+9-49-6-7-2+9+6)^{32} & := (-4-29+49-6+7+2-9-6)^{16} \\ & := (-42+9+49-6-7-2+9+6)^8 & := (-4-29+49+6+7+2-9-6)^8 \\ & := (42+9-49-6+7-2+9+6)^8 & := (-4-29+49-6-7-2+9-6)^{16} \\ & := (-42-9+49-6-7+2+9+6)^{32} & := (-4-29+49+6-7-2+9-6)^8 \\ & := (42-9-49-6+7+2+9+6)^{32} & := (4-29+49-6-7+2+9-6)^8 \\ & := (-42-9+49-6+7+2+9+6)^8 & := (4+29-49+6+7+2+9-6)^{32} \\ & := (-42+9-4-9+67-2-9-6)^{16} & := (-4-29+49-6-7+2-9+6)^{32} \\ & := (-42-9-4+9+67-2-9-6)^{16} & := (-4-29+49-6+7+2-9+6)^8 \\ & := (-42+9+4-9+67+2-9-6)^8 & := (-4-29+49-6-7-2+9+6)^8 \\ & := (-42-9+4+9+67+2-9-6)^8 & := (-4+29-49+6+7-2+9+6)^{32} \\ & := (-42-9-4-9+67-2+9-6)^{16} & := (4+29-49-6+7+2+9+6)^{32} \\ & := (42+9+4+9-67+2+9-6)^{32} & := (-4-29-4-9+67-2-9-6)^{16} \\ & := (-42-9+4-9+67+2+9-6)^8 & := (4-29-4-9+67+2-9-6)^8 \\ & := (-42+9-4-9+67-2-9+6)^8 & := (-4-29+4-9+67+2-9-6)^8 \\ & := (-42-9-4+9+67-2-9+6)^8 & := (-4-29-4-9+67-2-9+6)^8 \\ & := (-42-9-4-9+67+2-9+6)^{32} & := (4+29-4+9+6-7-29-6)^{32} \\ & := (42+9-4+9-67-2+9+6)^{32} & := (-4+29+4+9+6-7-29-6)^{32} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} &:= (4 + 29 - 4 + 9 - 6 + 7 - 29 - 6)^{16} & &:= (-4 + 2 + 94 - 96 + 7 - 2 + 9 + 6)^8 \\ &:= (-4 + 29 + 4 + 9 - 6 + 7 - 29 - 6)^{16} & &:= (-4 - 2 - 94 + 96 + 7 - 2 + 9 + 6)^8 \\ &:= (4 + 29 - 4 + 9 + 6 + 7 - 29 - 6)^8 & &:= (-4 - 2 + 94 - 96 - 7 + 2 + 9 + 6)^{32} \\ &:= (-4 + 29 + 4 + 9 + 6 + 7 - 29 - 6)^8 & &:= (-4 - 2 + 94 - 96 + 7 + 2 + 9 + 6)^8 \\ &:= (4 - 29 - 4 + 9 + 6 - 7 + 29 - 6)^{32} & &:= (-4 - 2 + 94 + 9 - 6 - 72 - 9 - 6)^{16} \\ &:= (-4 - 29 + 4 + 9 + 6 - 7 + 29 - 6)^{32} & &:= (4 + 2 + 94 + 9 - 6 - 72 - 9 - 6)^8 \\ &:= (4 - 29 - 4 + 9 - 6 + 7 + 29 - 6)^{16} & &:= (-4 + 2 + 94 - 9 + 6 - 72 - 9 - 6)^{32} \\ &:= (-4 - 29 + 4 + 9 - 6 + 7 + 29 - 6)^{16} & &:= (-4 - 2 + 94 + 9 + 6 - 72 - 9 - 6)^8 \\ &:= (4 - 29 - 4 + 9 + 6 + 7 + 29 - 6)^8 & &:= (-4 - 2 + 94 - 9 - 6 - 72 + 9 - 6)^{16} \\ &:= (-4 - 29 + 4 + 9 + 6 + 7 + 29 - 6)^8 & &:= (4 + 2 + 94 - 9 - 6 - 72 + 9 - 6)^8 \\ &:= (4 + 29 - 4 + 9 - 6 - 7 - 29 + 6)^{32} & &:= (-4 - 2 + 94 - 9 + 6 - 72 + 9 - 6)^8 \\ &:= (-4 + 29 + 4 + 9 - 6 - 7 - 29 + 6)^{32} & &:= (4 + 2 - 94 + 9 + 6 + 72 + 9 - 6)^{32} \\ &:= (4 + 29 + 4 - 9 + 6 - 7 - 29 + 6)^{16} & &:= (-4 + 2 + 94 - 9 - 6 - 72 - 9 + 6)^{32} \\ &:= (4 + 29 - 4 + 9 - 6 + 7 - 29 + 6)^8 & &:= (-4 - 2 + 94 + 9 - 6 - 72 - 9 + 6)^8 \\ &:= (-4 + 29 + 4 + 9 - 6 + 7 - 29 + 6)^8 & &:= (-4 - 2 + 94 - 9 - 6 - 72 + 9 + 6)^8 \\ &:= (-4 + 29 - 4 - 9 + 6 + 7 - 29 + 6)^{32} & &:= (4 + 2 - 94 + 9 - 6 + 72 + 9 + 6)^{32} \\ &:= (4 - 29 - 4 + 9 - 6 - 7 + 29 + 6)^{32} & &:= (-4 - 2 - 94 + 9 + 6 + 72 + 9 + 6)^{32} \\ &:= (-4 - 29 + 4 + 9 - 6 - 7 + 29 + 6)^{32} & &:= (-4 + 2 + 94 + 9 + 6 - 7 - 2 - 96)^{32} \\ &:= (4 - 29 + 4 - 9 + 6 - 7 + 29 + 6)^{16} & &:= (-4 + 2 + 94 + 9 - 6 + 7 - 2 - 96)^{16} \\ &:= (4 - 29 - 4 + 9 - 6 + 7 + 29 + 6)^8 & &:= (4 - 2 + 94 - 9 + 6 + 7 - 2 - 96)^{32} \\ &:= (-4 - 29 + 4 + 9 - 6 + 7 + 29 + 6)^8 & &:= (-4 + 2 + 94 + 9 + 6 + 7 - 2 - 96)^8 \\ &:= (-4 - 29 - 4 - 9 + 6 + 7 + 29 + 6)^{32} & &:= (4 + 2 + 94 + 9 - 6 - 7 + 2 - 96)^{32} \\ &:= (4 + 2 - 94 + 96 + 7 + 2 - 9 - 6)^{32} & &:= (-4 - 2 + 94 + 9 + 6 - 7 + 2 - 96)^{32} \\ &:= (4 + 2 - 94 + 96 - 7 - 2 + 9 - 6)^{32} & &:= (-4 - 2 + 94 + 9 - 6 + 7 + 2 - 96)^{16} \\ &:= (-4 + 2 + 94 - 96 + 7 - 2 + 9 - 6)^{16} & &:= (4 + 2 + 94 + 9 - 6 + 7 + 2 - 96)^8 \\ &:= (-4 - 2 - 94 + 96 + 7 - 2 + 9 - 6)^{16} & &:= (-4 + 2 + 94 - 9 + 6 + 7 + 2 - 96)^{32} \\ &:= (4 + 2 - 94 + 96 + 7 - 2 + 9 - 6)^8 & &:= (-4 - 2 + 94 + 9 + 6 + 7 + 2 - 96)^8 \\ &:= (4 + 2 + 94 - 96 - 7 + 2 + 9 - 6)^{32} & &:= (4 + 2 - 94 + 9 - 6 - 7 - 2 + 96)^{32} \\ &:= (4 - 2 - 94 + 96 - 7 + 2 + 9 - 6)^{32} & &:= (-4 - 2 - 94 + 9 + 6 - 7 - 2 + 96)^{32} \\ &:= (-4 - 2 + 94 - 96 + 7 + 2 + 9 - 6)^{16} & &:= (-4 - 2 - 94 + 9 - 6 + 7 - 2 + 96)^{16} \\ &:= (4 + 2 + 94 - 96 + 7 + 2 + 9 - 6)^8 & &:= (4 + 2 - 94 + 9 - 6 + 7 - 2 + 96)^8 \\ &:= (4 - 2 - 94 + 96 + 7 + 2 + 9 - 6)^8 & &:= (-4 + 2 - 94 - 9 + 6 + 7 - 2 + 96)^{32} \\ &:= (4 - 2 + 94 - 96 + 7 - 2 - 9 + 6)^{32} & &:= (-4 - 2 - 94 + 9 + 6 + 7 - 2 + 96)^8 \\ &:= (-4 + 2 - 94 + 96 + 7 - 2 - 9 + 6)^{32} & &:= (4 - 2 - 94 + 9 - 6 - 7 + 2 + 96)^{32} \\ &:= (-4 + 2 + 94 - 96 + 7 + 2 - 9 + 6)^{32} & &:= (4 + 2 - 94 - 9 - 6 + 7 + 2 + 96)^{32} \\ &:= (-4 - 2 - 94 + 96 + 7 + 2 - 9 + 6)^{32} & &:= (4 - 2 - 94 + 9 - 6 + 7 + 2 + 96)^8 \\ &:= (-4 + 2 + 94 - 96 - 7 - 2 + 9 + 6)^{32} & &:= (-4 - 2 - 94 - 9 + 6 + 7 + 2 + 96)^{32} \\ &:= (-4 - 2 - 94 + 96 - 7 - 2 + 9 + 6)^{32} & &:= (-4 - 2 + 9 - 49 + 67 - 2 - 9 - 6)^{16} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} &:= (4+2+9-49+67-2-9-6)^8 & &:= (4-2-9+4+96+7-2-96)^{32} \\ &:= (4+2-9-49+67+2-9-6)^{32} & &:= (-4+2+9+4+96+7-2-96)^8 \\ &:= (4-2+9-49+67+2-9-6)^8 & &:= (4-2+9-4+96-7+2-96)^{32} \\ &:= (-4-2-9-49+67-2+9-6)^{16} & &:= (-4-2+9+4+96-7+2-96)^{32} \\ &:= (4+2-9-49+67-2+9-6)^8 & &:= (4+2-9-4+96+7+2-96)^{32} \\ &:= (4+2+9+49-67+2+9-6)^{32} & &:= (4-2+9-4+96+7+2-96)^8 \\ &:= (4-2-9-49+67+2+9-6)^8 & &:= (-4+2-9+4+96+7+2-96)^{32} \\ &:= (-4+2-9-49+67-2-9+6)^{32} & &:= (-4-2+9+4+96+7+2-96)^8 \\ &:= (-4-2+9-49+67-2-9+6)^8 & &:= (4+2+9-4-96-7-2+96)^{32} \\ &:= (-4-2-9-49+67+2-9+6)^{32} & &:= (-4+2+9+4-96-7-2+96)^{32} \\ &:= (-4+2+9+49-67-2+9+6)^{32} & &:= (-4-2+9-4-96+7-2+96)^{16} \\ &:= (-4-2-9-49+67-2+9+6)^8 & &:= (4+2+9-4-96+7-2+96)^8 \\ &:= (-4-2+9+49-67+2+9+6)^{32} & &:= (4-2-9+4-96+7-2+96)^{32} \\ &:= (-4-2+9+49-6-7-29-6)^{16} & &:= (-4+2+9+4-96+7-2+96)^8 \\ &:= (4+2+9+49-6-7-29-6)^8 & &:= (4-2+9-4-96-7+2+96)^{32} \\ &:= (-4+2-9+49+6-7-29-6)^{32} & &:= (-4-2+9+4-96-7+2+96)^{32} \\ &:= (-4-2+9+49+6-7-29-6)^8 & &:= (4+2-9-4-96+7+2+96)^{32} \\ &:= (-4+2-9+49-6+7-29-6)^{16} & &:= (4-2+9-4-96+7+2+96)^8 \\ &:= (-4+2-9+49+6+7-29-6)^8 & &:= (-4+2-9+4-96+7+2+96)^{32} \\ &:= (4+2+9-49+6+7+29-6)^{32} & &:= (-4-2+9+4-96+7+2+96)^8 \\ &:= (-4+2-9+49-6-7-29+6)^{32} & &:= (-4-2-9-4-9+67-29-6)^{16} \\ &:= (-4-2+9+49-6-7-29+6)^8 & &:= (4+2-9-4-9+67-29-6)^8 \\ &:= (-4+2-9+49-6+7-29+6)^8 & &:= (-4+2-9+4-9+67-29-6)^8 \\ &:= (4+2+9-49-6+7+29+6)^{32} & &:= (-4-2-9-4-9+67-29+6)^8 \\ &:= (-4-2+9-49+6+7+29+6)^{32} & &:= (4+2+9-4+9+6+72-96)^{32} \\ &:= (4+2-9-4+96-72-9-6)^{32} & &:= (-4+2+9+4+9+6+72-96)^{32} \\ &:= (4-2+9-4+96-72-9-6)^8 & &:= (4+2-9-4-9-6-72+96)^{32} \\ &:= (-4+2-9+4+96-72-9-6)^{32} & &:= (4-2+9-4-9-6-72+96)^8 \\ &:= (-4-2+9+4+96-72-9-6)^8 & &:= (-4+2-9+4-9-6-72+96)^{32} \\ &:= (4-2-9-4+96-72+9-6)^8 & &:= (-4-2+9+4-9-6-72+96)^8 \\ &:= (-4-2-9+4+96-72+9-6)^8 & &:= (4-2-9-4+9-6-72+96)^8 \\ &:= (-4-2-9-4+96-72-9+6)^{32} & &:= (-4-2-9+4+9-6-72+96)^8 \\ &:= (4+2+9-4-96+72+9+6)^{32} & &:= (-4-2-9-4-9+6-72+96)^{32} \\ &:= (-4+2+9+4-96+72+9+6)^{32} & &:= (42+94-96-7-2-9-6)^8 \\ &:= (4+2+9-4+96-7-2-96)^{32} & &:= (42+94+96+7+2+9+6)^4 \\ &:= (-4+2+9+4+96-7-2-96)^{32} & &:= (42-94-9+6+72-9-6)^{32} \\ &:= (-4-2+9-4+96+7-2-96)^{16} & &:= (42-94-9-6+72-9+6)^{32} \\ &:= (4+2+9-4+96+7-2-96)^8 & &:= (42+94-9-6-7-2-96)^8 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 & := (42 + 94 + 9 + 6 + 7 + 2 + 96)^4 & := (-4 - 29 - 4 + 9 + 6 - 72 + 96)^{32} \\
 & := (42 + 9 + 49 - 67 - 2 - 9 - 6)^8 & := (4 - 2 + 94 - 96 - 7 + 29 - 6)^8 \\
 & := (42 - 9 + 49 - 67 + 2 - 9 - 6)^{32} & := (-4 + 2 - 94 + 96 - 7 + 29 - 6)^8 \\
 & := (42 - 9 + 49 - 67 - 2 + 9 - 6)^8 & := (4 + 2 + 94 - 9 + 67 + 2 + 96)^4 \\
 & := (-42 + 9 - 49 + 67 + 2 + 9 + 6)^{32} & := (4 + 2 - 9 + 49 - 67 + 29 - 6)^{32} \\
 & := (42 + 9 + 4 - 96 + 72 - 9 - 6)^8 & := (4 - 2 + 9 + 49 - 67 + 29 - 6)^8 \\
 & := (42 - 9 + 4 - 96 + 72 + 9 - 6)^8 & := (-4 + 2 + 9 - 49 + 67 - 29 + 6)^{32} \\
 & := (42 - 9 - 4 - 96 + 72 - 9 + 6)^{32} & := (-4 - 2 - 9 + 49 - 67 + 29 + 6)^{32} \\
 & := (-42 + 9 - 4 + 96 - 72 + 9 + 6)^{32} & := (-4 - 2 - 9 + 49 - 6 + 72 - 96)^{16} \\
 & := (42 + 9 + 4 + 96 + 7 + 2 + 96)^4 & := (4 + 2 - 9 + 49 - 6 + 72 - 96)^8 \\
 & := (-42 + 9 - 4 + 9 + 67 - 29 - 6)^{16} & := (-4 - 2 - 9 + 49 + 6 + 72 - 96)^8 \\
 & := (42 + 9 + 4 - 9 - 67 + 29 - 6)^{32} & := (42 - 94 + 96 - 7 - 29 - 6)^{32} \\
 & := (42 - 9 + 4 + 9 - 67 + 29 - 6)^{32} & := (42 - 94 + 96 + 7 - 29 - 6)^8 \\
 & := (-42 + 9 - 4 + 9 + 67 - 29 + 6)^8 & := (-42 - 94 + 96 + 7 + 29 + 6)^{32} \\
 & := (42 + 9 + 4 - 9 - 6 + 72 - 96)^8 & := (-42 + 94 - 9 + 67 + 2 - 96)^8 \\
 & := (42 - 9 + 4 + 9 - 6 + 72 - 96)^8 & := (-42 - 94 - 9 + 67 - 2 + 96)^8 \\
 & := (42 - 9 - 4 - 9 + 6 + 72 - 96)^{32} & := (42 - 9 - 49 + 67 - 29 - 6)^8 \\
 & := (-42 + 9 - 4 + 9 + 6 - 72 + 96)^{32} & := (-42 - 9 - 49 + 67 + 29 + 6)^{32} \\
 & := (4 + 294 + 9 + 6 - 72 + 9 + 6)^4 & := (42 - 9 - 49 - 6 - 72 + 96)^{32} \\
 & := (4 + 29 + 49 - 67 + 2 - 9 - 6)^{32} & := (-42 - 9 + 49 - 6 - 72 + 96)^8 \\
 & := (4 + 29 + 49 - 67 - 2 + 9 - 6)^8 & := (42 - 9 + 49 + 6 + 72 + 96)^4 \\
 & := (-4 + 29 + 49 - 67 - 2 - 9 + 6)^{32} & := (-4 + 294 + 9 + 6 - 7 - 296)^{32} \\
 & := (-4 - 29 - 49 + 67 + 2 + 9 + 6)^{32} & := (-4 + 294 + 9 - 6 + 7 - 296)^{16} \\
 & := (4 - 29 + 49 + 6 + 7 - 29 - 6)^{32} & := (-4 + 294 + 9 + 6 + 7 - 296)^8 \\
 & := (4 - 29 + 49 - 6 + 7 - 29 + 6)^{32} & := (4 - 294 + 9 - 6 - 7 + 296)^{32} \\
 & := (4 + 29 + 4 - 96 + 72 + 9 - 6)^8 & := (4 - 294 + 9 - 6 + 7 + 296)^8 \\
 & := (4 + 29 - 4 - 96 + 72 - 9 + 6)^{32} & := (-4 - 294 - 9 + 6 + 7 + 296)^{32} \\
 & := (-4 + 29 + 4 - 96 + 72 - 9 + 6)^{32} & := (4 + 29 - 49 + 67 - 29 - 6)^8 \\
 & := (-4 - 29 - 4 + 96 - 72 + 9 + 6)^{32} & := (4 - 29 - 49 + 67 + 29 - 6)^8 \\
 & := (-4 + 29 - 4 + 96 - 7 + 2 - 96)^8 & := (4 + 29 - 49 - 6 - 72 + 96)^{32} \\
 & := (-4 + 29 - 4 - 96 - 7 + 2 + 96)^8 & := (4 + 29 + 49 + 6 + 72 + 96)^4 \\
 & := (4 - 29 + 4 - 9 + 67 - 29 - 6)^{32} & := (-4 - 2 + 949 - 672 - 9 - 6)^4 \\
 & := (-4 - 29 - 4 + 9 + 67 - 29 - 6)^{16} & := (-4 - 2 + 94 + 96 - 72 - 96)^8 \\
 & := (4 + 29 + 4 + 9 - 67 + 29 - 6)^{32} & := (-4 - 2 + 94 - 96 - 72 + 96)^8 \\
 & := (-4 - 29 - 4 + 9 + 67 - 29 + 6)^8 & := (429 - 496 + 72 - 9 + 6)^{32} \\
 & := (4 + 29 + 4 + 9 - 6 + 72 - 96)^8 & := (42 + 94 - 96 + 72 - 96)^8 \\
 & := (4 + 29 - 4 - 9 + 6 + 72 - 96)^{32} & := (42 + 94 + 96 - 72 + 96)^4 \\
 & := (-4 + 29 + 4 - 9 + 6 + 72 - 96)^{32} & := **4314825152** := (-4 + 3 + 1482 - 5 + 152)^3
 \end{aligned}$$

$$:= (43 + 1482 + 51 + 52)^3$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{4356660025} &:= (4 + 3 - 5 + 6 + 66002 - 5)^2 \\ &:= (-4 + 3 + 5 - 6 + 66002 + 5)^2 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{4362470401} &:= (4 - 3 + 6 + 247 + 04 - 01)^4 \\ &:= (4 + 3 + 6 + 247 - 04 + 01)^4 \\ &:= (-4 + 3 + 6 + 247 + 04 + 01)^4 \\ &:= (43 + 6 + 247 - 040 + 1)^4 \end{aligned}$$

$$\mathbf{4386781853} := (4 - 3 + 8 - 6 + 781 + 853)^3$$

$$\mathbf{4393966369} := (-4 - 39 - 39 + 66369)^2$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{4430766096} &:= (4 + 4 + 307 + 6 - 60 - 9 + 6)^4 \\ &:= (-44 - 307 + 6 + 609 - 6)^4 \\ &:= (-44 - 307 - 6 + 609 + 6)^4 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{4437053125} &:= (4 + 4 + 3 + 70 + 5 + 3 - 1 + 2 - 5)^5 \\ &:= (4 + 4 + 3 + 70 + 5 - 3 - 1 - 2 + 5)^5 \\ &:= (4 + 4 - 3 + 70 + 5 + 3 - 1 - 2 + 5)^5 \\ &:= (4 - 4 + 3 + 70 + 5 + 3 + 1 - 2 + 5)^5 \\ &:= (-4 + 4 + 3 + 70 + 5 + 3 + 1 - 2 + 5)^5 \\ &:= (4 + 4 + 3 + 70 - 5 + 3 - 1 + 2 + 5)^5 \\ &:= (4 + 4 - 3 + 70 + 5 - 3 + 1 + 2 + 5)^5 \\ &:= (44 + 37 + 05 + 3 - 1 + 2 - 5)^5 \\ &:= (44 + 37 + 05 - 3 - 1 - 2 + 5)^5 \\ &:= (44 + 37 - 05 + 3 - 1 + 2 + 5)^5 \\ &:= (44 + 3 - 7 + 053 - 1 - 2 - 5)^5 \\ &:= (44 - 3 - 7 + 053 + 1 + 2 - 5)^5 \\ &:= (4 + 43 - 7 + 053 - 1 - 2 - 5)^5 \\ &:= (-4 + 43 + 7 + 05 + 31 - 2 + 5)^5 \\ &:= (-4 - 4 - 3 + 70 + 5 - 3 - 1 + 25)^5 \\ &:= (4 - 4 - 3 + 70 - 5 - 3 + 1 + 25)^5 \\ &:= (-4 + 4 - 3 + 70 - 5 - 3 + 1 + 25)^5 \\ &:= (44 + 3 + 70 - 5 - 3 + 1 - 25)^5 \\ &:= (44 - 3 + 70 - 5 + 3 + 1 - 25)^5 \\ &:= (44 - 3 - 7 - 05 + 31 + 25)^5 \\ &:= (-44 + 3 - 7 + 05 + 3 + 125)^5 \\ &:= (-4 + 43 + 70 + 5 - 3 - 1 - 25)^5 \\ &:= (4 + 43 + 70 - 5 - 3 + 1 - 25)^5 \\ &:= (4 - 43 + 7 - 05 - 3 + 125)^5 \end{aligned}$$

$$\mathbf{4466783556} := (4 - 4 + 66783 - 5 + 56)^2$$

$$\mathbf{4466783556} := (-4 + 4 + 66783 - 5 + 56)^2$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{4481766916} &:= (44 - 8 + 1 - 7 + 66916)^2 \\ &:= (-44 + 81 - 7 + 66916)^2 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{4499860561} &:= (4 + 4 + 99 + 86 + 05 + 61)^4 \\ &:= (44 - 9 + 98 + 60 + 5 + 61)^4 \\ &:= (-4 + 49 + 98 + 60 - 5 + 61)^4 \\ &:= (-449 + 98 + 605 + 6 - 1)^4 \end{aligned}$$

$$\mathbf{4506705424} := (4 + 50 + 67054 + 24)^2$$

$$\mathbf{4526732961} := (-45 + 2 + 67329 - 6 + 1)^2$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{4586471424} &:= (4 - 5 + 8 + 6 - 4 + 7 + 14 - 2 - 4)^7 \\ &:= (-4 - 5 + 8 + 6 + 4 + 7 + 14 - 2 - 4)^7 \\ &:= (4 + 5 + 8 + 6 - 4 - 7 + 14 + 2 - 4)^7 \\ &:= (-4 + 5 + 8 + 6 + 4 - 7 + 14 + 2 - 4)^7 \\ &:= (4 - 5 + 8 - 6 + 4 + 7 + 14 + 2 - 4)^7 \\ &:= (4 + 5 + 8 - 6 + 4 - 7 + 14 - 2 + 4)^7 \\ &:= (-4 - 5 + 8 + 6 - 4 + 7 + 14 - 2 + 4)^7 \\ &:= (4 - 5 - 8 + 6 + 4 + 7 + 14 - 2 + 4)^7 \\ &:= (-4 + 5 + 8 + 6 - 4 - 7 + 14 + 2 + 4)^7 \\ &:= (4 + 5 - 8 + 6 + 4 - 7 + 14 + 2 + 4)^7 \\ &:= (4 - 5 + 8 - 6 - 4 + 7 + 14 + 2 + 4)^7 \\ &:= (-4 - 5 + 8 - 6 + 4 + 7 + 14 + 2 + 4)^7 \\ &:= (45 + 8 - 6 + 4 - 7 - 14 - 2 - 4)^7 \\ &:= (45 - 8 + 6 + 4 - 7 - 14 + 2 - 4)^7 \\ &:= (45 + 8 - 6 - 4 - 7 - 14 - 2 + 4)^7 \\ &:= (45 - 8 + 6 - 4 - 7 - 14 + 2 + 4)^7 \\ &:= (4 - 58 + 64 + 7 + 1 + 4 - 2 + 4)^7 \\ &:= (4 + 58 + 6 - 47 + 1 + 4 + 2 - 4)^7 \\ &:= (4 + 58 + 6 - 47 + 1 - 4 + 2 + 4)^7 \\ &:= (-4 + 58 + 6 - 47 + 1 + 4 + 2 + 4)^7 \\ &:= (4 + 58 + 6 - 4 + 7 - 1 - 42 - 4)^7 \\ &:= (-4 + 58 + 6 + 4 + 7 - 1 - 42 - 4)^7 \\ &:= (-4 + 58 + 6 - 4 + 7 - 1 - 42 + 4)^7 \\ &:= (4 + 58 - 6 + 4 - 7 - 1 - 4 - 24)^7 \\ &:= (-4 + 58 - 6 - 4 + 7 + 1 - 4 - 24)^7 \\ &:= (4 + 58 - 6 - 4 - 7 - 1 + 4 - 24)^7 \\ &:= (-4 + 58 - 6 + 4 - 7 - 1 + 4 - 24)^7 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 & := (471 - 199 - 8 + 7 - 3 - 6)^4 & & := (47 - 50 - 1 + 042 + 4 - 1)^6 \\
 & := (47 + 119 + 98 + 7 - 3 - 6)^4 & & := (-47 + 50 - 1 + 042 - 4 + 1)^6 \\
 & := (47 + 119 + 9 + 8 + 73 + 6)^4 & & := (47 - 50 + 1 + 04 - 2 + 41)^6 \\
 & := (4 - 711 - 9 + 987 - 3 - 6)^4 & & := (-47 + 50 - 1 - 04 + 2 + 41)^6 \\
 & := (4 + 7 + 119 + 9 + 87 + 36)^4 & & := (47 + 5 + 010 + 4 - 24 - 1)^6 \\
 & := (4 + 7 + 1 + 199 + 87 - 36)^4 & & := (-4 - 7 + 50 + 1 + 042 - 41)^6 \\
 & := (4 - 711 + 998 + 7 - 36)^4 & & := (47 + 5 - 010 - 42 + 41)^6 \\
 & := (4 + 7 - 11 + 998 - 736)^4 & & := (-47 - 5 + 010 + 42 + 41)^6 \\
 & := (-4 - 7 + 11 + 998 - 736)^4 & & \\
 \mathbf{4736880625} & := (4 - 7 - 3 + 68806 + 25)^2 & & \mathbf{4753688809} := (4 + 75 - 3 + 68880 - 9)^2 \\
 & := (47 - 3 + 68806 - 25)^2 & & \mathbf{4758586568} := (-4 + 758 - 5 + 865 + 68)^3 \\
 \mathbf{4750104241} & := (-4 + 7 + 50 - 1 - 04 - 2 - 4 - 1)^6 & & \mathbf{4761690025} := (-4 + 7 + 6 - 1 + 69002 - 5)^2 \\
 & := (4 - 7 + 50 + 1 - 04 + 2 - 4 - 1)^6 & & & := (-4 + 7 - 6 + 1 + 69002 + 5)^2 \\
 & := (-4 - 7 + 50 + 1 + 04 + 2 - 4 - 1)^6 & & \mathbf{4767078987} := (4 + 767 + 07 + 898 + 7)^3 \\
 & := (-4 - 7 + 50 + 1 - 04 + 2 + 4 - 1)^6 & & & := (4 + 7 + 670 + 7 + 8 + 987)^3 \\
 & := (4 - 7 + 50 - 1 - 04 + 2 - 4 + 1)^6 & & & := (-4 + 7 - 6 + 707 - 8 + 987)^3 \\
 & := (-4 - 7 + 50 - 1 + 04 + 2 - 4 + 1)^6 & & \mathbf{4769007364} := (4 + 7 + 69007 + 36 + 4)^2 \\
 & := (-4 - 7 + 50 - 1 - 04 + 2 + 4 + 1)^6 & & \mathbf{4775581504} := (47 + 75 + 58 + 1504)^3 \\
 & := (47 - 5 + 010 - 4 - 2 - 4 - 1)^6 & & \mathbf{4782690649} := (4 + 78 + 2 + 69064 + 9)^2 \\
 & := (47 - 5 - 010 + 4 + 2 + 4 - 1)^6 & & \mathbf{4784350561} := (4 - 7 - 84 + 350 - 5 + 6 - 1)^4 \\
 & := (47 + 5 - 010 + 4 - 2 - 4 + 1)^6 & & & := (4 - 7 - 84 + 350 + 5 - 6 + 1)^4 \\
 & := (47 + 5 - 010 - 4 - 2 + 4 + 1)^6 & & & := (478 - 4 + 350 - 561)^4 \\
 & := (4 + 75 + 01 - 042 + 4 - 1)^6 & & \mathbf{4806926224} := (-4 + 80 + 69262 - 2 - 4)^2 \\
 & := (4 + 75 - 01 - 042 + 4 + 1)^6 & & \mathbf{4814694544} := (-48 - 14 + 69454 - 4)^2 \\
 & := (-4 + 75 - 01 - 04 - 24 - 1)^6 & & \mathbf{4819969476} := (48 + 1 - 99 + 69476)^2 \\
 & := (4 + 75 + 01 + 04 - 2 - 41)^6 & & \mathbf{4833169441} := (48 + 33 - 1 + 69441)^2 \\
 & := (4 + 7 + 50 + 1 + 04 - 24 - 1)^6 & & \mathbf{4853769561} := (48 + 53 + 7 + 69561)^2 \\
 & := (4 + 7 + 50 - 1 + 04 - 24 + 1)^6 & & \mathbf{4857532416} := (-48 + 5 - 7 - 5 + 324 + 1 - 6)^4 \\
 & := (-4 - 7 + 5 + 010 + 42 - 4 - 1)^6 & & & := (-48 - 5 - 7 + 5 + 324 + 1 - 6)^4 \\
 & := (4 + 7 - 5 - 010 + 42 + 4 - 1)^6 & & & := (-48 - 5 - 7 - 5 + 324 - 1 + 6)^4 \\
 & := (4 - 7 - 5 + 010 + 42 - 4 + 1)^6 & & & := (-4 - 8 - 5 - 7 + 53 + 241 - 6)^4 \\
 & := (-4 - 7 - 5 + 010 + 42 + 4 + 1)^6 & & & := (-48 + 57 + 5 + 3 + 241 + 6)^4 \\
 & := (4 - 7 + 5 + 010 + 4 + 24 + 1)^6 & & & := (-48 + 5 + 75 - 3 + 241 - 6)^4 \\
 & := (4 + 7 + 5 - 010 - 4 - 2 + 41)^6 & & & := (-48 + 5 + 7 + 53 + 241 + 6)^4 \\
 & := (-4 + 7 + 5 - 010 + 4 - 2 + 41)^6 & & & := (4 + 85 - 75 + 3 + 241 + 6)^4 \\
 & := (4 - 7 - 5 + 010 - 4 + 2 + 41)^6 & & & := (4 + 85 - 7 - 53 + 241 - 6)^4 \\
 & := (-4 - 7 - 5 + 010 + 4 + 2 + 41)^6 & & & := (-4 + 8 - 5 - 75 + 324 + 16)^4 \\
 & := (-47 + 50 + 1 + 042 - 4 - 1)^6 & & \mathbf{4861163384} := (4 + 8 + 61 + 1633 - 8 - 4)^3 \\
 & & & & := (4 - 8 + 61 + 1633 + 8 - 4)^3
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 & := (-4 + 8 + 61 + 1633 - 8 + 4)^3 \\
 & := (-4 - 8 + 61 + 1633 + 8 + 4)^3 \\
 \mathbf{4887035873} & := (-48 + 870 - 3 + 5 + 873)^3 \\
 \mathbf{4921675101} & := (4 + 9 + 2 + 1675 + 10 + 1)^3 \\
 & := (-4 + 9216 - 7510 - 1)^3 \\
 & := (4 + 921 + 675 + 101)^3 \\
 \mathbf{4930360408} & := (4 + 930 + 360 + 408)^3 \\
 \mathbf{4931269729} & := (493 - 1 + 2 + 69729)^2 \\
 \mathbf{4931550625} & := (4 + 93 + 155 + 06 + 2 + 5)^4 \\
 & := (4 + 9 + 315 - 50 - 6 - 2 - 5)^4 \\
 & := (-4 - 9 + 315 - 50 + 6 + 2 + 5)^4 \\
 & := (4 + 931 + 5 - 50 - 625)^4 \\
 & := (-4 + 9 - 315 - 50 + 625)^4 \\
 & := (49 - 315 + 506 + 25)^4 \\
 \mathbf{4937170225} & := (49 - 3 - 7 + 1 + 70225)^2 \\
 \mathbf{4947761664} & := (4 + 947 + 761 - 6 - 6 + 4)^3 \\
 \mathbf{4984209207} & := (-4 + 9 + 84 - 2 + 09 - 2 - 07)^5 \\
 & := (-4 + 9 + 84 + 2 - 09 - 2 + 07)^5 \\
 & := (-4 - 9 + 84 + 2 + 09 - 2 + 07)^5 \\
 & := (-4 + 9 + 84 - 2 - 09 + 2 + 07)^5 \\
 & := (-4 - 9 + 84 - 2 + 09 + 2 + 07)^5 \\
 & := (49 - 8 + 42 + 09 + 2 - 07)^5 \\
 & := (49 + 8 - 4 + 20 + 9 - 2 + 07)^5 \\
 & := (49 + 8 - 4 - 2 + 09 + 20 + 7)^5 \\
 & := (-4 - 9 + 84 + 20 - 9 - 2 + 07)^5 \\
 & := (-4 + 9 + 84 - 20 + 9 + 2 + 07)^5 \\
 & := (-4 + 9 + 84 + 2 + 09 - 20 + 7)^5 \\
 & := (-4 - 9 + 84 - 2 - 09 + 20 + 7)^5 \\
 & := (49 - 8 + 42 - 09 + 20 - 7)^5 \\
 & := (49 - 8 + 4 + 20 + 9 + 20 - 7)^5 \\
 & := (-4 + 9 + 84 + 20 - 9 - 20 + 7)^5 \\
 & := (-4 - 9 + 84 + 20 + 9 - 20 + 7)^5 \\
 & := (-4 + 9 + 84 - 20 - 9 + 20 + 7)^5 \\
 & := (-4 - 9 + 84 - 20 + 9 + 20 + 7)^5 \\
 & := (-4 + 984 + 20 - 920 + 7)^5 \\
 & := (-4 + 9 + 84 - 209 + 207)^5 \\
 \mathbf{5017776128} & := (-50 + 1777 - 6 + 1 - 2 - 8)^3 \\
 \mathbf{5041710025} & := (5 + 04 - 1 + 71002 - 5)^2
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 & := (-5 + 04 - 1 + 71002 + 5)^2 \\
 \mathbf{5073712900} & := (-50 - 7 - 3 + 71290 + 0)^2 \\
 \mathbf{5082121521} & := (50 + 8 + 212 + 1 - 5 + 2 - 1)^4 \\
 & := (50 + 8 + 212 - 1 - 5 + 2 + 1)^4 \\
 & := (50 + 8 - 2 - 1 + 215 - 2 - 1)^4 \\
 & := (-5 + 08 + 212 + 1 + 52 - 1)^4 \\
 & := (-5 + 08 + 212 - 1 + 52 + 1)^4 \\
 & := (-50 + 82 - 1 + 215 + 21)^4 \\
 \mathbf{5106219048} & := (-510 - 6 + 2190 + 48)^3 \\
 \mathbf{5131716496} & := (5 - 13 + 1 + 71649 - 6)^2 \\
 & := (-5 - 13 - 1 + 71649 + 6)^2 \\
 \mathbf{5158686976} & := (5 + 158 + 6 + 8 + 6 + 9 + 76)^4 \\
 & := (5 + 1 + 5 + 86 + 86 + 9 + 76)^4 \\
 & := (51 + 58 + 68 + 6 + 9 + 76)^4 \\
 & := (51 + 58 + 6 + 86 - 9 + 76)^4 \\
 & := (51 + 58 + 6 + 8 + 69 + 76)^4 \\
 & := (-515 + 868 + 6 - 97 + 6)^4 \\
 \mathbf{5159780352} & := (51 - 5 - 9 - 7 - 8 - 03 - 5 - 2)^9 \\
 & := (-5 + 15 - 9 + 7 + 8 + 03 - 5 - 2)^9 \\
 & := (5 + 15 - 9 - 7 + 8 - 03 + 5 - 2)^9 \\
 & := (-5 + 15 + 9 + 7 - 8 - 03 - 5 + 2)^9 \\
 & := (5 + 15 - 9 - 7 + 8 + 03 - 5 + 2)^9 \\
 & := (-5 + 15 - 9 - 7 + 8 + 03 + 5 + 2)^9 \\
 & := (-5 - 1 - 5 - 9 + 7 - 8 + 035 - 2)^9 \\
 & := (5 - 1 - 5 - 9 - 7 - 8 + 035 + 2)^9 \\
 & := (-5 - 1 + 5 - 9 - 7 - 8 + 035 + 2)^9 \\
 & := (-51 - 5 - 9 + 7 + 80 - 3 - 5 - 2)^9 \\
 & := (-51 + 5 - 9 - 7 + 80 - 3 - 5 + 2)^9 \\
 & := (-51 - 5 - 9 - 7 + 80 - 3 + 5 + 2)^9 \\
 & := (-5 - 1 - 59 + 7 + 80 - 3 - 5 - 2)^9 \\
 & := (5 - 1 - 59 - 7 + 80 - 3 - 5 + 2)^9 \\
 & := (-5 - 1 - 59 - 7 + 80 - 3 + 5 + 2)^9 \\
 & := (5 - 1 - 5 + 97 - 80 + 3 - 5 - 2)^9 \\
 & := (-5 - 1 + 5 + 97 - 80 + 3 - 5 - 2)^9 \\
 & := (-5 - 1 - 5 + 97 - 80 + 3 + 5 - 2)^9 \\
 & := (5 + 1 - 5 + 97 - 80 - 3 - 5 + 2)^9 \\
 & := (-5 + 1 + 5 + 97 - 80 - 3 - 5 + 2)^9 \\
 & := (-5 + 1 - 5 + 97 - 80 - 3 + 5 + 2)^9
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 & := (-5 - 1 - 5 - 9 + 7 + 80 - 3 - 52)^9 & := (5 - 2 + 77 - 3 + 1 + 9 - 1 - 6 + 8)^5 \\
 & := (-51 - 5 + 97 + 8 - 035 - 2)^9 & := (-5 + 2 + 77 + 3 + 1 + 9 - 1 - 6 + 8)^5 \\
 & := (51 - 5 - 97 + 8 + 03 + 52)^9 & := (5 - 2 + 77 - 3 - 1 + 9 + 1 - 6 + 8)^5 \\
 & := (-5 - 15 - 9 + 78 - 035 - 2)^9 & := (-5 + 2 + 77 + 3 - 1 + 9 + 1 - 6 + 8)^5 \\
 & := (-5 - 15 + 9 + 78 - 03 - 52)^9 & := (5 - 2 + 77 + 3 + 1 - 9 - 1 + 6 + 8)^5 \\
 & := (-5 - 1 + 59 - 78 + 035 + 2)^9 & := (-5 - 2 + 77 - 3 - 1 + 9 - 1 + 6 + 8)^5 \\
 & := (-51 - 59 - 7 + 80 - 3 + 52)^9 & := (5 - 2 + 77 + 3 - 1 - 9 + 1 + 6 + 8)^5 \\
 & := (-5 + 159 - 7 - 80 - 3 - 52)^9 & := (5 + 2 + 77 - 3 + 1 - 9 + 1 + 6 + 8)^5 \\
 & := (-5 - 15 - 97 + 80 - 3 + 52)^9 & := (5 - 2 + 7 + 73 - 1 + 9 - 1 + 6 - 8)^5 \\
 \mathbf{5165871876} & := (-5 + 16 - 5 - 8 + 71876)^2 & := (-5 + 2 + 7 + 73 + 1 + 9 - 1 - 6 + 8)^5 \\
 \mathbf{5168743489} & := (5 + 1687 + 4 + 34 + 8 - 9)^3 & := (-5 + 2 + 7 + 73 - 1 + 9 + 1 - 6 + 8)^5 \\
 & := (-5 + 1687 - 4 + 34 + 8 + 9)^3 & := (5 - 2 + 7 + 73 + 1 - 9 - 1 + 6 + 8)^5 \\
 & := (516 + 874 + 348 - 9)^3 & := (5 - 2 + 7 + 73 - 1 - 9 + 1 + 6 + 8)^5 \\
 \mathbf{5171911056} & := (5 + 1 + 71911 + 05 - 6)^2 & := (-5 + 2 - 7 + 73 + 1 + 9 + 1 + 6 + 8)^5 \\
 & := (5 - 1 + 71911 - 05 + 6)^2 & := (5 + 2 + 7 - 7 + 3 + 1 + 91 - 6 - 8)^5 \\
 & := (-5 - 1 + 71911 + 05 + 6)^2 & := (5 + 2 - 7 + 7 + 3 + 1 + 91 - 6 - 8)^5 \\
 & := (-51 + 71911 + 056)^2 & := (-5 - 2 + 7 + 7 + 3 + 1 + 91 - 6 - 8)^5 \\
 \mathbf{5177717000} & := (51 - 7 - 7 - 7 + 1700 + 0)^3 & := (5 - 2 + 7 - 7 - 3 - 1 + 91 + 6 - 8)^5 \\
 \mathbf{5184720025} & := (5 - 1 + 8 - 4 + 72002 - 5)^2 & := (5 - 2 - 7 + 7 - 3 - 1 + 91 + 6 - 8)^5 \\
 & := (-5 + 1 + 8 + 4 + 72002 - 5)^2 & := (-5 + 2 + 7 - 7 + 3 - 1 + 91 + 6 - 8)^5 \\
 & := (-5 - 1 + 8 - 4 + 72002 + 5)^2 & := (-5 + 2 - 7 + 7 + 3 - 1 + 91 + 6 - 8)^5 \\
 \mathbf{5186700891} & := (-5186 + 7008 - 91)^3 & := (5 + 2 - 7 - 7 + 3 - 1 + 91 - 6 + 8)^5 \\
 \mathbf{5231776256} & := (-52 + 3 + 1776 - 2 + 5 + 6)^3 & := (-5 - 2 + 7 - 7 + 3 - 1 + 91 - 6 + 8)^5 \\
 & := (-5 + 23 + 1776 - 2 - 56)^3 & := (-5 - 2 - 7 + 7 + 3 - 1 + 91 - 6 + 8)^5 \\
 \mathbf{5236114321} & := (-5 + 236 - 1 - 1 + 43 - 2 - 1)^4 & := (-5 + 2 + 7 - 7 - 3 + 1 + 91 - 6 + 8)^5 \\
 & := (5 + 236 + 1 - 1 + 4 + 3 + 21)^4 & := (-5 + 2 - 7 + 7 - 3 + 1 + 91 - 6 + 8)^5 \\
 & := (5 + 236 - 1 + 1 + 4 + 3 + 21)^4 & := (-5 - 2 - 7 - 7 + 3 + 1 + 91 + 6 + 8)^5 \\
 & := (5 - 2 + 3 - 61 - 1 + 4 + 321)^4 & := (-5 + 27 + 73 - 1 + 9 - 1 - 6 - 8)^5 \\
 & := (5 + 2 - 3 - 61 + 1 + 4 + 321)^4 & := (-5 + 27 + 73 + 1 - 9 - 1 - 6 + 8)^5 \\
 & := (-5 + 236 + 11 - 4 + 32 - 1)^4 & := (-5 + 27 + 73 - 1 - 9 + 1 - 6 + 8)^5 \\
 & := (-5 + 2 - 36 + 1 - 14 + 321)^4 & := (-5 + 27 - 7 - 3 - 1 + 91 - 6 - 8)^5 \\
 & := (52 + 361 - 143 - 2 + 1)^4 & := (5 - 27 + 7 - 3 + 1 + 91 + 6 + 8)^5 \\
 \mathbf{5272502544} & := (52 + 72502 + 54 + 4)^2 & := (-5 + 2 + 7 - 7 + 31 - 9 + 1 + 68)^5 \\
 \mathbf{5277112021} & := (-5 - 277 + 1 + 1 + 2021)^3 & := (-5 + 2 - 7 + 7 + 31 - 9 + 1 + 68)^5 \\
 \mathbf{5277319168} & := (52 + 7 + 7 - 3 + 1 + 9 + 1 + 6 + 8)^5 & := (-5 - 2 - 7 - 7 + 31 + 9 + 1 + 68)^5 \\
 & := (5 - 2 + 77 + 3 - 1 + 9 - 1 + 6 - 8)^5 & := (5 - 2 + 7 - 7 - 3 + 19 + 1 + 68)^5 \\
 & := (5 + 2 + 77 - 3 + 1 + 9 - 1 + 6 - 8)^5 & := (5 - 2 - 7 + 7 - 3 + 19 + 1 + 68)^5 \\
 & := (5 + 2 + 77 - 3 - 1 + 9 + 1 + 6 - 8)^5 & := (-5 + 2 + 7 - 7 + 3 + 19 + 1 + 68)^5
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 & := (-5 + 2 - 7 + 7 + 3 + 19 + 1 + 68)^5 \\
 & := (52 + 77 - 31 - 9 + 1 + 6 - 8)^5 \\
 & := (-5 + 2 + 77 + 31 - 9 - 16 + 8)^5 \\
 & := (5 - 2 + 77 - 3 + 19 - 16 + 8)^5 \\
 & := (-5 + 2 + 77 + 3 + 19 - 16 + 8)^5 \\
 & := (5 - 2 + 77 + 3 - 19 + 16 + 8)^5 \\
 & := (-5 + 2 + 7 + 73 + 19 - 16 + 8)^5 \\
 & := (5 - 2 + 7 + 73 - 19 + 16 + 8)^5 \\
 & := (-52 + 7 + 7 + 3 + 191 - 68)^5 \\
 & := (-5 - 27 - 73 + 191 - 6 + 8)^5 \\
 & := (5 - 2 + 77 + 31 - 91 + 68)^5 \\
 & := (-5 + 277 + 3 - 19 - 168)^5 \\
 \mathbf{5285726209} & := (5 + 2 + 85 + 72620 - 9)^2 \\
 \mathbf{5287325796} & := (-528 + 73257 - 9 - 6)^2 \\
 \mathbf{5322708936} & := (532 + 270 + 8 + 936)^3 \\
 \mathbf{5333673024} & := (5 + 3 + 3 + 3 - 6 + 73024)^2 \\
 & := (5 + 3 - 3 - 3 + 6 + 73024)^2 \\
 & := (5 - 3 + 3 - 3 + 6 + 73024)^2 \\
 & := (5 - 3 - 3 + 3 + 6 + 73024)^2 \\
 & := (5 - 33 + 36 + 73024)^2 \\
 \mathbf{5393580481} & := (5 + 3 + 93 + 5 + 80 + 4 + 81)^4 \\
 \mathbf{5444373796} & := (5 - 4 - 4 - 4 - 3 + 73796)^2 \\
 \mathbf{5473632256} & := (-5 + 4 + 7 + 3 + 6 + 3 - 2 + 256)^4 \\
 & := (5 - 4 + 7 + 3 + 6 - 3 + 2 + 256)^4 \\
 & := (5 - 4 + 7 - 3 + 6 + 3 + 2 + 256)^4 \\
 & := (5 + 4 - 7 + 3 + 6 + 3 + 2 + 256)^4 \\
 & := (54 - 7 + 3 + 6 - 3 + 225 - 6)^4 \\
 & := (54 - 7 - 3 + 6 + 3 + 225 - 6)^4 \\
 & := (54 - 7 + 3 - 6 - 3 + 225 + 6)^4 \\
 & := (54 - 7 - 3 - 6 + 3 + 225 + 6)^4 \\
 & := (5 - 47 - 3 + 6 + 322 - 5 - 6)^4 \\
 & := (-5 - 47 - 3 + 6 + 322 + 5 - 6)^4 \\
 & := (5 - 47 - 3 - 6 + 322 - 5 + 6)^4 \\
 & := (-5 - 47 - 3 - 6 + 322 + 5 + 6)^4 \\
 & := (5 - 4 + 7 + 36 - 3 + 225 + 6)^4 \\
 & := (5 + 4 - 7 + 36 + 3 + 225 + 6)^4 \\
 & := (54 - 7 - 36 + 3 + 2 + 256)^4 \\
 & := (5 - 47 - 3 + 63 - 2 + 256)^4 \\
 & := (-5 - 47 + 3 + 63 + 2 + 256)^4 \\
 & := (547 + 36 - 322 + 5 + 6)^4 \\
 & := (547 - 3 - 6 - 322 + 56)^4 \\
 & := (-5 + 47 - 36 + 322 - 56)^4 \\
 & := (-5 - 47 + 36 + 32 + 256)^4 \\
 \mathbf{5473928196} & := (54 + 73928 + 1 + 9 - 6)^2 \\
 \mathbf{5476740025} & := (5 + 4 - 7 + 6 + 74002 - 5)^2 \\
 & := (-5 + 4 - 7 + 6 + 74002 + 5)^2 \\
 \mathbf{5489031744} & := (54 - 8 + 9 + 03 - 1 - 7 - 4 - 4)^6 \\
 & := (54 + 8 - 9 + 03 + 1 - 7 - 4 - 4)^6 \\
 & := (54 + 8 - 9 - 03 - 1 - 7 + 4 - 4)^6 \\
 & := (54 - 8 - 9 - 03 + 1 + 7 + 4 - 4)^6 \\
 & := (54 + 8 - 9 - 03 - 1 - 7 - 4 + 4)^6 \\
 & := (54 - 8 - 9 - 03 + 1 + 7 - 4 + 4)^6 \\
 & := (54 - 8 - 9 + 03 + 1 - 7 + 4 + 4)^6 \\
 & := (5 + 4 + 8 + 9 + 031 - 7 - 4 - 4)^6 \\
 & := (5 - 4 + 8 + 9 + 031 - 7 + 4 - 4)^6 \\
 & := (5 - 4 + 8 + 9 + 031 - 7 - 4 + 4)^6 \\
 & := (5 + 4 - 8 + 9 + 031 - 7 + 4 + 4)^6 \\
 & := (-5 - 4 - 8 - 9 - 03 + 1 + 74 - 4)^6 \\
 & := (5 - 48 + 90 - 3 - 1 + 7 - 4 - 4)^6 \\
 & := (5 - 48 + 90 + 3 - 1 - 7 + 4 - 4)^6 \\
 & := (-5 - 48 + 90 - 3 + 1 + 7 + 4 - 4)^6 \\
 & := (5 - 48 + 90 + 3 - 1 - 7 - 4 + 4)^6 \\
 & := (-5 - 48 + 90 - 3 + 1 + 7 + 4 - 4)^6 \\
 & := (-5 - 48 + 90 - 3 + 1 + 7 - 4 + 4)^6 \\
 & := (-5 - 48 + 90 + 3 + 1 - 7 + 4 + 4)^6 \\
 & := (5 + 48 + 9 - 03 - 17 + 4 - 4)^6 \\
 & := (5 + 48 + 9 - 03 - 17 - 4 + 4)^6 \\
 & := (5 - 48 + 9 - 03 + 1 + 74 + 4)^6 \\
 & := (-5 + 4 + 89 - 031 - 7 - 4 - 4)^6 \\
 & := (-5 - 4 + 89 - 031 - 7 + 4 - 4)^6 \\
 & := (-5 - 4 + 89 - 031 - 7 - 4 + 4)^6 \\
 & := (-5 + 4 + 8 + 90 - 3 - 1 - 7 - 44)^6 \\
 & := (5 + 4 - 8 + 90 + 3 - 1 - 7 - 44)^6 \\
 & := (-5 - 4 + 8 + 90 + 3 + 1 - 7 - 44)^6 \\
 & := (5 - 4 - 8 + 90 - 3 - 1 + 7 - 44)^6 \\
 & := (-5 + 4 - 8 + 90 - 3 + 1 + 7 - 44)^6 \\
 & := (-5 - 4 - 8 - 9 + 031 - 7 + 44)^6
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 \mathbf{5601816576} &:= (5 + 6 + 01816 - 57 + 6)^3 & & := (5 - 9 + 1 + 991 + 812 + 9)^3 \\
 \mathbf{5620762952} &:= (5 - 6 + 2076 - 295 - 2)^3 & & \mathbf{5947648641} := (594 + 76486 + 41)^2 \\
 \mathbf{5625750025} &:= (5 + 6 + 2 - 5 + 75002 - 5)^2 & & \mathbf{5949419328} := (-5 - 94 - 9 - 4 + 1932 - 8)^3 \\
 &:= (-5 + 6 + 2 + 5 + 75002 - 5)^2 & & & := (-5 - 9 - 4 - 94 + 1932 - 8)^3 \\
 &:= (-5 + 6 + 2 - 5 + 75002 + 5)^2 & & & := (-59 - 49 - 4 + 1932 - 8)^3 \\
 \mathbf{5636405776} &:= (-5 - 63 + 6 + 405 + 7 - 76)^4 & & \mathbf{5972816656} := (59 + 72 - 8 + 166 - 5 - 6)^4 \\
 \mathbf{5637757225} &:= (5 - 637 + 75722 - 5)^2 & & & := (59 - 7 + 281 - 66 + 5 + 6)^4 \\
 &:= (-5 - 637 + 75722 + 5)^2 & & & := (59 + 7 - 2 - 8 + 166 + 56)^4 \\
 \mathbf{5674759561} &:= (5 + 6 + 74759 + 561)^2 & & & := (5 + 9 - 7 + 281 - 66 + 56)^4 \\
 \mathbf{5678376025} &:= (5 - 678 + 3 + 76025)^2 & & \mathbf{5979018375} := (5 + 979 - 01 + 837 - 5)^3 \\
 \mathbf{5719140625} &:= (57 + 191 + 40 - 6 - 2 - 5)^4 & & \mathbf{5979018375} := (-5 + 979 - 01 + 837 + 5)^3 \\
 &:= (57 + 191 - 4 + 06 + 25)^4 & & \mathbf{5998805513} := (5 + 998 + 805 + 5 + 1 + 3)^3 \\
 &:= (57 - 191 + 406 - 2 + 5)^4 & & \mathbf{6039776656} := (6 + 039 + 77665 + 6)^2 \\
 &:= (57 + 191 - 40 + 62 + 5)^4 & & \mathbf{6049417284} := (60494 + 17284)^2 \\
 \mathbf{5758381456} &:= (-5 + 75838 - 1 - 4 + 56)^2 & & \mathbf{6059221281} := (60 + 5 + 9 + 2 + 212 - 8 - 1)^4 \\
 \mathbf{5758988544} &:= (-5 + 75898 + 8 - 5 - 4 - 4)^2 & & & := (60 + 5 - 9 + 2 + 212 + 8 + 1)^4 \\
 &:= (-5 + 75898 - 8 - 5 + 4 + 4)^2 & & & := (6 + 059 + 221 + 2 - 8 - 1)^4 \\
 \mathbf{5763694561} &:= (5 + 76369 - 456 + 1)^2 & & & := (-6 + 059 + 221 - 2 + 8 - 1)^4 \\
 \mathbf{5768098704} &:= (5 + 76809 - 870 + 4)^2 & & & := (-60 + 59 + 2 - 2 - 1 + 281)^4 \\
 \mathbf{5802782976} &:= (580 - 2 - 7 + 8 - 297 - 6)^4 & & & := (-60 + 59 - 2 + 2 - 1 + 281)^4 \\
 &:= (580 + 2 - 7 - 8 - 297 + 6)^4 & & & := (60 - 59 - 2 - 2 + 1 + 281)^4 \\
 &:= (5 + 80 + 278 - 2 - 9 - 76)^4 & & \mathbf{6067786816} := (6 + 06 + 77868 + 16)^2 \\
 &:= (-5 - 80 + 278 - 2 + 9 + 76)^4 & & \mathbf{6077917521} := (60 + 77917 + 5 - 21)^2 \\
 \mathbf{5804154225} &:= (-5 + 80415 - 4225)^2 & & \mathbf{6084780025} := (-6 + 08 - 4 + 78002 + 5)^2 \\
 \mathbf{5822285399} &:= (-582 + 2285 - 3 + 99)^3 & & \mathbf{6103515625} := (6 + 10 + 3 + 5 - 1 - 5 - 6 - 2 - 5)^{14} \\
 &:= (-5 - 82 + 2285 - 399)^3 & & & := (6 + 10 + 3 - 5 - 1 + 5 - 6 - 2 - 5)^{14} \\
 \mathbf{5827642921} &:= (-5 - 82 + 76429 - 2 - 1)^2 & & & := (-6 + 10 + 3 + 5 + 1 + 5 - 6 - 2 - 5)^{14} \\
 \mathbf{5841725401} &:= (-5 + 84 + 1725 - 4 + 01)^3 & & & := (-6 + 10 + 3 + 5 - 1 - 5 + 6 - 2 - 5)^{14} \\
 \mathbf{5887339441} &:= (58 + 87 + 33 + 94 + 4 + 1)^4 & & & := (-6 + 10 + 3 - 5 - 1 + 5 + 6 - 2 - 5)^{14} \\
 &:= (58 + 8 + 73 + 3 + 94 + 41)^4 & & & := (6 + 10 - 3 + 5 + 1 - 5 - 6 + 2 - 5)^{14} \\
 &:= (-58 - 8 - 7 - 3 + 394 - 41)^4 & & & := (6 + 10 - 3 - 5 + 1 + 5 - 6 + 2 - 5)^{14} \\
 \mathbf{5904900000} &:= (5 + 90 + 4 - 9 + 0000 + 0)^5 & & & := (6 + 10 - 3 - 5 - 1 - 5 + 6 + 2 - 5)^{14} \\
 &:= (-5 + 90 - 4 + 9 + 0000 + 0)^5 & & & := (-6 + 10 - 3 + 5 + 1 - 5 + 6 + 2 - 5)^{14} \\
 &:= (-5 + 9 - 04 + 90 + 0000)^5 & & & := (6 - 10 - 3 + 5 - 1 + 5 + 6 + 2 - 5)^{14} \\
 &:= (5 - 9 + 04 + 90 + 0000)^5 & & & := (6 + 10 - 3 + 5 - 1 + 5 + 6 + 2 - 5)^7 \\
 \mathbf{5906076201} &:= (590 + 60 + 76201)^2 & & & := (-6 + 10 - 3 - 5 + 1 + 5 + 6 + 2 - 5)^{14} \\
 \mathbf{5919918129} &:= (5 - 9 + 19 - 9 + 1812 - 9)^3 & & & := (6 + 10 + 3 - 5 - 1 - 5 - 6 - 2 + 5)^{14} \\
 &:= (5 + 9 + 1 + 991 + 812 - 9)^3 & & & := (-6 + 10 + 3 + 5 + 1 - 5 - 6 - 2 + 5)^{14}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} & := (6 - 10 + 3 + 5 - 1 + 5 - 6 - 2 + 5)^{14} & := (61 - 035 + 1 - 5 + 6 + 2 - 5)^7 \\ & := (6 + 10 + 3 + 5 - 1 + 5 - 6 - 2 + 5)^7 & := (61 + 03 - 51 + 5 - 6 - 2 - 5)^{14} \\ & := (-6 + 10 + 3 - 5 + 1 + 5 - 6 - 2 + 5)^{14} & := (61 - 03 - 51 - 5 + 6 + 2 - 5)^{14} \\ & := (-6 + 10 + 3 - 5 - 1 - 5 + 6 - 2 + 5)^{14} & := (61 + 03 - 51 - 5 - 6 - 2 + 5)^{14} \\ & := (-6 - 10 + 3 + 5 - 1 + 5 + 6 - 2 + 5)^{14} & := (61 - 03 - 51 + 5 + 6 + 2 + 5)^7 \\ & := (-6 + 10 + 3 + 5 - 1 + 5 + 6 - 2 + 5)^7 & := (-61 - 03 + 51 + 5 + 6 + 2 + 5)^{14} \\ & := (6 + 10 - 3 - 5 + 1 - 5 - 6 + 2 + 5)^{14} & := (61 - 03 - 5 - 15 - 6 - 2 - 5)^7 \\ & := (6 - 10 - 3 + 5 + 1 + 5 - 6 + 2 + 5)^{14} & := (61 + 03 + 5 - 1 - 56 - 2 - 5)^{14} \\ & := (6 + 10 - 3 + 5 + 1 + 5 - 6 + 2 + 5)^7 & := (61 - 03 + 5 + 1 - 56 + 2 - 5)^{14} \\ & := (6 - 10 - 3 + 5 - 1 - 5 + 6 + 2 + 5)^{14} & := (61 + 03 - 5 - 1 - 56 - 2 + 5)^{14} \\ & := (6 + 10 - 3 + 5 - 1 - 5 + 6 + 2 + 5)^7 & := (-61 + 03 + 5 - 1 + 56 - 2 + 5)^{14} \\ & := (-6 + 10 - 3 - 5 + 1 - 5 + 6 + 2 + 5)^{14} & := (61 - 03 - 5 + 1 - 56 + 2 + 5)^{14} \\ & := (6 - 10 - 3 - 5 - 1 + 5 + 6 + 2 + 5)^{14} & := (-61 - 03 + 5 + 1 + 56 + 2 + 5)^{14} \\ & := (6 + 10 - 3 - 5 - 1 + 5 + 6 + 2 + 5)^7 & := (6 + 10 - 3 + 5 + 1 + 5 + 6 - 25)^{14} \\ & := (-6 - 10 - 3 + 5 + 1 + 5 + 6 + 2 + 5)^{14} & := (-6 - 10 + 3 + 5 - 1 - 5 - 6 + 25)^{14} \\ & := (-6 + 10 - 3 + 5 + 1 + 5 + 6 + 2 + 5)^7 & := (-6 + 10 + 3 + 5 - 1 - 5 - 6 + 25)^7 \\ & := (6 + 1 + 035 + 1 - 5 - 6 - 2 - 5)^7 & := (-6 - 10 + 3 - 5 - 1 + 5 - 6 + 25)^{14} \\ & := (-6 + 1 + 035 + 1 - 5 + 6 - 2 - 5)^7 & := (-6 + 10 + 3 - 5 - 1 + 5 - 6 + 25)^7 \\ & := (6 - 1 + 035 - 1 - 5 - 6 + 2 - 5)^7 & := (6 - 10 - 3 + 5 + 1 - 5 + 6 + 25)^7 \\ & := (-6 + 1 + 035 - 1 + 5 - 6 + 2 - 5)^7 & := (6 - 10 - 3 - 5 + 1 + 5 + 6 + 25)^7 \\ & := (-6 - 1 + 035 + 1 + 5 - 6 + 2 - 5)^7 & := (6 + 1 - 035 + 1 - 5 + 62 - 5)^7 \\ & := (-6 - 1 + 035 - 1 - 5 + 6 + 2 - 5)^7 & := (6 + 1 + 035 - 1 - 5 - 6 - 25)^{14} \\ & := (-6 + 1 + 035 - 1 - 5 - 6 + 2 + 5)^7 & := (6 - 1 + 035 + 1 - 5 - 6 - 25)^{14} \\ & := (-6 - 1 + 035 + 1 - 5 - 6 + 2 + 5)^7 & := (-6 + 1 + 035 + 1 + 5 - 6 - 25)^{14} \\ & := (-6 + 1 - 03 + 51 - 5 - 6 - 2 - 5)^7 & := (-6 + 1 + 035 - 1 - 5 + 6 - 25)^{14} \\ & := (6 - 1 + 03 - 5 + 15 - 6 - 2 - 5)^{14} & := (-6 - 1 + 035 + 1 - 5 + 6 - 25)^{14} \\ & := (-6 + 1 + 03 + 5 + 15 - 6 - 2 - 5)^{14} & := (6 - 1 + 035 - 1 + 5 + 6 - 25)^7 \\ & := (-6 - 1 + 03 - 5 + 15 + 6 - 2 - 5)^{14} & := (6 - 1 - 035 - 1 + 5 + 6 + 25)^{14} \\ & := (6 + 1 - 03 - 5 + 15 - 6 + 2 - 5)^{14} & := (6 + 1 - 03 - 51 - 5 + 62 - 5)^{14} \\ & := (-6 + 1 - 03 - 5 + 15 + 6 + 2 - 5)^{14} & := (6 + 1 - 03 - 51 + 5 + 62 + 5)^7 \\ & := (6 - 1 - 03 + 5 + 15 + 6 + 2 - 5)^7 & := (-6 - 1 - 03 + 51 - 5 - 6 - 25)^{14} \\ & := (-6 + 1 + 03 - 5 + 15 - 6 - 2 + 5)^{14} & := (6 + 1 + 03 + 51 - 5 - 6 - 25)^7 \\ & := (6 - 1 + 03 + 5 + 15 - 6 - 2 + 5)^7 & := (-6 + 1 + 03 + 51 - 5 + 6 - 25)^7 \\ & := (-6 - 1 + 03 + 5 + 15 + 6 - 2 + 5)^7 & := (6 + 1 - 03 + 5 + 15 + 6 - 25)^{14} \\ & := (6 + 1 - 03 + 5 + 15 - 6 + 2 + 5)^7 & := (-6 - 1 + 03 + 5 - 15 - 6 + 25)^{14} \\ & := (6 - 1 - 03 + 5 - 15 + 6 + 2 + 5)^{14} & := (-6 - 1 + 03 - 5 + 15 - 6 + 25)^7 \\ & := (6 - 1 - 03 - 5 + 15 + 6 + 2 + 5)^7 & := (6 + 1 - 03 + 5 - 15 + 6 + 25)^7 \\ & := (-6 + 1 - 03 + 5 + 15 + 6 + 2 + 5)^7 & := (-6 - 1 - 03 + 5 - 1 + 56 - 25)^7 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 & := (-6 + 1 + 03 - 5 + 1 + 56 - 25)^7 \\
 & := (61 + 035 + 1 - 5 - 62 - 5)^7 \\
 & := (-61 + 035 - 1 - 5 + 62 - 5)^7 \\
 & := (61 + 03 - 5 - 15 + 6 - 25)^7 \\
 & := (-6 - 10 + 35 + 15 - 6 + 2 - 5)^7 \\
 & := (6 - 10 + 35 - 15 + 6 - 2 + 5)^7 \\
 & := (6 + 10 - 35 + 15 + 6 - 2 + 5)^{14} \\
 & := (-6 - 10 + 35 - 15 - 6 + 2 + 5)^{14} \\
 & := (-6 + 10 + 35 - 15 - 6 + 2 + 5)^7 \\
 & := (6 - 10 - 35 + 1 + 56 + 2 + 5)^7 \\
 & := (-6 + 10 + 3 - 51 + 56 - 2 - 5)^{14} \\
 & := (6 + 10 - 3 + 51 - 56 + 2 - 5)^{14} \\
 & := (-6 + 10 + 3 + 51 - 56 - 2 + 5)^{14} \\
 & := (6 - 10 - 3 - 51 + 56 + 2 + 5)^{14} \\
 & := (6 + 10 - 3 - 51 + 56 + 2 + 5)^7 \\
 & := (6 + 103 - 51 - 56 - 2 + 5)^{14} \\
 & := (-6 - 103 + 51 + 56 + 2 + 5)^{14} \\
 & := (6 + 10 + 35 - 15 - 6 - 25)^{14} \\
 & := (-6 + 10 + 35 - 15 + 6 - 25)^{14} \\
 & := (610 - 3 - 515 - 62 - 5)^7 \\
 & := (610 + 3 - 51 - 562 + 5)^{14} \\
 & := (-610 - 3 + 51 + 562 + 5)^{14} \\
 & := (610 + 35 - 15 - 625)^{14} \\
 \mathbf{6138539191} & := (61 - 3 + 853 + 919 + 1)^3 \\
 \mathbf{6144678544} & := (-6 - 144 - 6 + 78544)^2 \\
 \mathbf{6157854784} & := (-6 + 15 + 78547 - 84)^2 \\
 \mathbf{6168761704} & := (61 + 68 + 7 - 6 + 1704)^3 \\
 \mathbf{6178857875} & := (-6 + 1788 + 57 + 8 - 7 - 5)^3 \\
 & := (61 + 7 + 885 + 7 + 875)^3 \\
 \mathbf{6178903236} & := (-61 + 78903 - 236)^2 \\
 \mathbf{6187867569} & := (-6 + 1 + 8 + 78675 - 6 - 9)^2 \\
 & := (-6 - 1 - 8 + 78675 - 6 + 9)^2 \\
 \mathbf{6199083253} & := (6 + 1 + 990 + 832 + 5 + 3)^3 \\
 \mathbf{6209212472} & := (-6 + 2092 + 1 - 247 - 2)^3 \\
 \mathbf{6227892889} & := (6 + 2 - 2 + 78928 - 8 - 9)^2 \\
 & := (6 - 2 + 2 + 78928 - 8 - 9)^2 \\
 & := (-6 - 2 - 2 + 78928 + 8 - 9)^2 \\
 & := (-6 - 22 + 78928 + 8 + 9)^2 \\
 \mathbf{6234839521} & := (-6 + 234 + 8 + 39 + 5 + 2 - 1)^4 \\
 & := (6 + 234 + 8 + 39 - 5 - 2 + 1)^4 \\
 & := (-6 + 234 + 8 + 3 - 9 + 52 - 1)^4 \\
 & := (-6 - 2 + 348 + 3 - 9 - 52 - 1)^4 \\
 & := (-6 + 2 + 348 - 3 - 9 - 52 + 1)^4 \\
 & := (-62 - 3 - 48 + 395 - 2 + 1)^4 \\
 & := (6 + 234 + 83 + 9 - 52 + 1)^4 \\
 & := (6 - 2 + 348 + 3 - 95 + 21)^4 \\
 \mathbf{6240321451} & := (62 - 4 + 032 + 1 - 4 + 5 - 1)^5 \\
 & := (62 + 4 + 032 + 1 - 4 - 5 + 1)^5 \\
 & := (62 - 4 + 032 + 1 + 4 - 5 + 1)^5 \\
 & := (62 - 4 + 032 - 1 - 4 + 5 + 1)^5 \\
 & := (62 + 4 + 03 + 2 + 14 + 5 + 1)^5 \\
 & := (6 + 24 + 03 + 2 + 1 + 4 + 51)^5 \\
 & := (6 + 2 + 40 + 32 + 1 + 4 + 5 + 1)^5 \\
 & := (6 - 2 + 40 + 3 - 2 - 1 - 4 + 51)^5 \\
 & := (6 + 2 + 40 - 3 - 2 + 1 - 4 + 51)^5 \\
 & := (6 - 2 + 40 - 3 + 2 + 1 - 4 + 51)^5 \\
 & := (-6 + 2 + 40 + 3 - 2 - 1 + 4 + 51)^5 \\
 & := (-6 - 2 + 40 + 3 + 2 - 1 + 4 + 51)^5 \\
 & := (-6 + 2 + 40 - 3 + 2 + 1 + 4 + 51)^5 \\
 & := (6 + 2 + 4 + 032 + 1 + 45 + 1)^5 \\
 & := (6 + 2 + 4 + 03 + 21 + 4 + 51)^5 \\
 & := (62 + 40 - 3 + 2 - 14 + 5 - 1)^5 \\
 & := (-62 + 4 + 03 + 2 + 145 - 1)^5 \\
 & := (-6 + 24 - 03 + 21 + 4 + 51)^5 \\
 & := (-6 - 2 - 40 - 3 - 2 + 145 - 1)^5 \\
 & := (62 + 40 + 32 + 1 - 45 + 1)^5 \\
 & := (62 - 4 - 032 + 14 + 51)^5 \\
 & := (-6 + 240 + 3 - 2 - 145 + 1)^5 \\
 & := (62 - 40 + 32 - 14 + 51)^5 \\
 \mathbf{6279294564} & := (6 + 2 + 79294 - 56 - 4)^2 \\
 \mathbf{6311112192} & := (631 + 1 - 1 + 1219 - 2)^3 \\
 & := (631 - 1 + 1 + 1219 - 2)^3 \\
 \mathbf{6321363049} & := (63 - 2 + 1 + 3 - 6 - 3 - 04 - 9)^6 \\
 & := (63 - 2 + 1 - 3 - 6 + 3 - 04 - 9)^6 \\
 & := (63 - 2 - 1 - 3 - 6 - 3 + 04 - 9)^6 \\
 & := (6 + 3 + 21 - 3 + 6 - 3 + 04 + 9)^6
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 &:= (6-3+21+3+6-3+04+9)^6 & &:= (6+3-2-13+6+30+4+9)^6 \\
 &:= (6+3+21+3-6+3+04+9)^6 & &:= (-6-3-2+1+36+30-4-9)^6 \\
 &:= (6-3+21-3+6+3+04+9)^6 & &:= (63-2+13-6-30-4+9)^6 \\
 &:= (-6+3+21+3+6+3+04+9)^6 & &:= (63-2+1-36+30-4-9)^6 \\
 &:= (-6+3-2+1-3+63-04-9)^6 & &:= (63-2-1-3-63+049)^6 \\
 &:= (-6-3-2+1+3+63-04-9)^6 & &:= (-63-2-1-3+63+049)^6 \\
 &:= (-6-3-2-1-3+63+04-9)^6 & &:= (-6-32+13+63-04+9)^6 \\
 &:= (6+3-2-1-3-6-3+049)^6 & &:= (-6-32-1+36-3+049)^6 \\
 &:= (6-3+2+1-3-6-3+049)^6 & &:= (-6+32+1-36+3+049)^6 \\
 &:= (6-3-2-1+3-6-3+049)^6 & &:= (-6+32+1+3-6-30+49)^6 \\
 &:= (-6+3+2+1+3-6-3+049)^6 & &:= (6-32-1-3-6+30+49)^6 \\
 &:= (-6+3-2-1-3+6-3+049)^6 & &:= (-6-32-1-3+6+30+49)^6 \\
 &:= (-6-3+2+1-3+6-3+049)^6 & &:= (6-3-21+36+30+4-9)^6 \\
 &:= (-6-3-2-1+3+6-3+049)^6 & &:= (6-3+21+36-30+4+9)^6 \\
 &:= (6-3-2-1-3-6+3+049)^6 & &:= (6-3+2+13+6-30+49)^6 \\
 &:= (-6+3+2+1-3-6+3+049)^6 & &:= (-6-3-2-1+36-30+49)^6 \\
 &:= (-6+3-2-1+3-6+3+049)^6 & &:= (6-3-2-1-36+30+49)^6 \\
 &:= (-6-3+2+1+3-6+3+049)^6 & &:= (-6+3+2+1-36+30+49)^6 \\
 &:= (-6-3-2-1-3+6+3+049)^6 & &:= (63-21+36-30+4-9)^6 \\
 &:= (63-21+3+6-3+04-9)^6 & &:= (63-2-1-36-30+49)^6 \\
 &:= (63-21-3+6+3+04-9)^6 & &:= (6-321+363+04-9)^6 \\
 &:= (63-21-3-6-3+04+9)^6 & &:= (6+3-21+36-30+49)^6 \\
 &:= (6+32+13-6+3+04-9)^6 & &:= (-632-1-3+630+49)^6 \\
 &:= (-6+32+13+6+3+04-9)^6 & &:= (-63-213+6+304+9)^6 \\
 &:= (-6+32+13-6-3+04+9)^6 & & & & \mathbf{6322794256} := (63+22+79425+6)^2 \\
 &:= (-6+32+1-3-6+30+4-9)^6 & & & & \mathbf{6324066576} := (6+324-066+5+7+6)^4 \\
 &:= (6+3-21-3+63+04-9)^6 & & & & := (6-3+240-6-6+57-6)^4 \\
 &:= (6-3-21+3+63+04-9)^6 & & & & := (-6-3+240+6-6+57-6)^4 \\
 &:= (-6-3-21-3+63+04+9)^6 & & & & := (-6-3+240-6+6+57-6)^4 \\
 &:= (6+3-21+3+6-3+049)^6 & & & & := (-6-3+240-6-6+57+6)^4 \\
 &:= (6+3-21-3+6+3+049)^6 & & & & \mathbf{6390083844} := (-6-3900+83844)^2 \\
 &:= (6-3-21+3+6+3+049)^6 & & & & \mathbf{6396800400} := (-63+9-6+80040+0)^2 \\
 &:= (6+3-2+13+6+30-4-9)^6 & & & & \mathbf{6398880049} := (-63-9+8+8+80049)^2 \\
 &:= (6+3+2+13-6+30+4-9)^6 & & & & \mathbf{6400480009} := (-6+4-004+80009)^2 \\
 &:= (-6+3+2+13+6+30+4-9)^6 & & & & := (-6-4+004+80009)^2 \\
 &:= (6-3-2+13-6+30-4+9)^6 & & & & \mathbf{6400800025} := (-6+4+0080002+5)^2 \\
 &:= (-6-3-2+13+6+30-4+9)^6 & & & & \mathbf{6404800900} := (-64+04+80090+0)^2 \\
 &:= (-6-3+2+13-6+30+4+9)^6 & & & & \mathbf{6414247921} := (6+4+14+247+9+2+1)^4
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 & := (-641 + 4 + 2 + 4 - 7 + 921)^4 \\
 & := (-64 + 1 + 424 - 79 + 2 - 1)^4 \\
 & := (-64 - 1 + 424 - 79 + 2 + 1)^4 \\
 & := (6 + 4 + 14 + 247 - 9 + 21)^4 \\
 & := (64 + 142 + 47 + 9 + 21)^4 \\
 \mathbf{6497329896} & := (-6 - 4 + 973 - 2 + 9 + 896)^3 \\
 \mathbf{6518244032} & := (-6 + 5 + 1824 + 40 + 3 + 2)^3 \\
 \mathbf{6528717909} & := (-6 + 5 + 2 + 87 + 1790 - 9)^3 \\
 \mathbf{6561810025} & := (6 - 5 + 6 + 1 + 81002 - 5)^2 \\
 \mathbf{6573804241} & := (657 - 3 + 80424 + 1)^2 \\
 \mathbf{6580129924} & := (65 + 80129 + 924)^2 \\
 \mathbf{6581103376} & := (6 + 5 + 81103 - 3 + 7 + 6)^2 \\
 \mathbf{6590815232} & := (6 + 5 + 90 - 8 + 1 + 5 - 2 - 3 - 2)^5 \\
 & := (6 - 5 + 90 + 8 + 1 - 5 + 2 - 3 - 2)^5 \\
 & := (6 - 5 + 90 + 8 - 1 - 5 - 2 + 3 - 2)^5 \\
 & := (-6 + 5 + 90 + 8 + 1 - 5 - 2 + 3 - 2)^5 \\
 & := (-6 - 5 + 90 + 8 + 1 + 5 - 2 + 3 - 2)^5 \\
 & := (6 + 5 + 90 - 8 + 1 - 5 + 2 + 3 - 2)^5 \\
 & := (6 - 5 + 90 - 8 + 1 + 5 + 2 + 3 - 2)^5 \\
 & := (6 - 5 + 90 + 8 + 1 - 5 - 2 - 3 + 2)^5 \\
 & := (-6 + 5 + 90 + 8 - 1 - 5 + 2 - 3 + 2)^5 \\
 & := (-6 - 5 + 90 + 8 - 1 + 5 + 2 - 3 + 2)^5 \\
 & := (6 + 5 + 90 - 8 + 1 - 5 - 2 + 3 + 2)^5 \\
 & := (6 - 5 + 90 - 8 + 1 + 5 - 2 + 3 + 2)^5 \\
 & := (-6 + 5 + 90 - 8 - 1 + 5 + 2 + 3 + 2)^5 \\
 & := (65 + 9 - 08 + 1 - 5 - 2 + 32)^5 \\
 & := (65 - 9 + 08 - 1 - 5 + 2 + 32)^5 \\
 & := (6 + 59 + 08 - 1 - 5 + 23 + 2)^5 \\
 & := (-6 + 59 + 08 + 1 + 5 + 23 + 2)^5 \\
 & := (6 + 5 + 90 + 8 - 1 + 5 - 23 + 2)^5 \\
 & := (-6 - 5 + 90 - 8 + 1 - 5 + 23 + 2)^5 \\
 & := (65 + 9 + 08 - 15 + 23 + 2)^5 \\
 & := (6 - 59 - 08 + 152 + 3 - 2)^5 \\
 & := (6 + 59 + 08 - 15 + 2 + 32)^5 \\
 & := (6 + 59 + 08 - 1 + 52 - 32)^5 \\
 & := (-6 - 5 + 90 - 8 + 1 + 52 - 32)^5 \\
 & := (-6 - 5 - 9 - 08 + 152 - 32)^5 \\
 & := (-6 + 5 + 90 - 81 + 52 + 32)^5 \\
 \mathbf{6591796875} & := (65 + 917 + 968 - 75)^3 \\
 \mathbf{6597500625} & := (-65 + 975 - 00625)^4 \\
 \mathbf{6646814784} & := (6 - 6 + 46 + 81478 + 4)^2 \\
 & := (-6 + 6 + 46 + 81478 + 4)^2 \\
 \mathbf{6690585616} & := (66 + 90 + 58 + 5 + 61 + 6)^4 \\
 & := (6 - 6 + 905 - 8 + 5 - 616)^4 \\
 & := (-6 + 6 + 905 - 8 + 5 - 616)^4 \\
 & := (66 + 90 + 58 + 56 + 16)^4 \\
 \mathbf{6697829125} & := (-6 - 6 + 978 + 2 + 912 + 5)^3 \\
 \mathbf{6731382025} & := (6 + 7 + 3 + 1 + 3 + 82025)^2 \\
 \mathbf{6761990971} & := (-6 - 76 + 1990 - 9 - 7 - 1)^3 \\
 & := (-6 - 7 - 6 + 1990 - 9 - 71)^3 \\
 \mathbf{6776582400} & := (-6 + 7 - 76 - 5 + 82400)^2 \\
 \mathbf{6784652161} & := (67 + 8 - 4 + 6 - 5 + 216 - 1)^4 \\
 & := (67 + 8 - 4 - 6 + 5 + 216 + 1)^4 \\
 & := (6 - 7 + 84 - 6 - 5 + 216 - 1)^4 \\
 & := (-6 - 7 + 84 + 6 - 5 + 216 - 1)^4 \\
 & := (-6 - 7 + 84 - 6 + 5 + 216 + 1)^4 \\
 & := (6 + 7 + 8 + 46 + 5 + 216 - 1)^4 \\
 & := (-6 + 7 + 8 - 4 + 65 + 216 + 1)^4 \\
 & := (67 - 8 + 4 + 65 - 2 + 161)^4 \\
 & := (6 + 78 - 4 - 6 + 52 + 161)^4 \\
 & := (-6 + 78 - 4 + 6 + 52 + 161)^4 \\
 & := (-6 + 784 - 652 + 161)^4 \\
 \mathbf{6816648969} & := (-6 + 81664 + 896 + 9)^2 \\
 \mathbf{6823751236} & := (-6 + 82375 + 1 + 236)^2 \\
 \mathbf{6825568689} & := (-6 + 82556 + 8 + 68 - 9)^2 \\
 \mathbf{6825899161} & := (6 + 82589 + 9 + 16 - 1)^2 \\
 \mathbf{6826064400} & := (6 + 82606 + 4 + 4 + 00)^2 \\
 \mathbf{6826725376} & := (6 + 82672 - 53 - 7 + 6)^2 \\
 \mathbf{6827055876} & := (-6 + 82705 - 5 + 8 - 76)^2 \\
 \mathbf{6827882161} & := (6 + 82788 - 2 - 161)^2 \\
 \mathbf{6832014336} & := (68320 + 14336)^2 \\
 \mathbf{6860643241} & := (6 + 86064 - 3241)^2 \\
 \mathbf{6879707136} & := (-687 + 970 + 7 + 1 + 3 - 6)^4 \\
 \mathbf{6891541327} & := (689 + 1541 - 327)^3 \\
 \mathbf{6924185416} & := (69 - 24 + 1854 + 1 + 6)^3 \\
 \mathbf{6956883693} & := (69 + 5 + 6 + 8 + 8 + 3 + 6 - 9 - 3)^5
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 &:= (69 + 5 + 6 + 8 + 8 - 3 - 6 + 9 - 3)^5 \\
 &:= (69 + 5 - 6 + 8 + 8 - 3 + 6 + 9 - 3)^5 \\
 &:= (69 + 5 + 6 + 8 + 8 - 3 + 6 - 9 + 3)^5 \\
 &:= (69 + 5 - 6 + 8 + 8 + 3 - 6 + 9 + 3)^5 \\
 &:= (6 + 9 + 5 + 68 + 8 + 3 + 6 - 9 - 3)^5 \\
 &:= (6 + 9 + 5 + 68 + 8 - 3 - 6 + 9 - 3)^5 \\
 &:= (-6 + 9 + 5 + 68 + 8 - 3 + 6 + 9 - 3)^5 \\
 &:= (6 - 9 + 5 + 68 + 8 + 3 + 6 + 9 - 3)^5 \\
 &:= (6 + 9 + 5 + 68 + 8 - 3 + 6 - 9 + 3)^5 \\
 &:= (-6 + 9 + 5 + 68 + 8 + 3 - 6 + 9 + 3)^5 \\
 &:= (6 - 9 + 5 + 68 + 8 - 3 + 6 + 9 + 3)^5 \\
 &:= (6 + 9 + 5 + 6 + 88 - 3 - 6 - 9 - 3)^5 \\
 &:= (6 + 9 + 5 - 6 + 88 - 3 + 6 - 9 - 3)^5 \\
 &:= (-6 + 9 + 5 + 6 + 88 - 3 + 6 - 9 - 3)^5 \\
 &:= (6 - 9 + 5 + 6 + 88 + 3 + 6 - 9 - 3)^5 \\
 &:= (6 - 9 + 5 + 6 + 88 - 3 - 6 + 9 - 3)^5 \\
 &:= (-6 + 9 + 5 - 6 + 88 + 3 - 6 + 9 - 3)^5 \\
 &:= (6 - 9 + 5 + 6 + 88 - 3 + 6 + 9 - 3)^5 \\
 &:= (-6 - 9 + 5 + 6 + 88 - 3 + 6 + 9 - 3)^5 \\
 &:= (6 + 9 + 5 - 6 + 88 + 3 - 6 - 9 + 3)^5 \\
 &:= (-6 + 9 + 5 + 6 + 88 + 3 - 6 - 9 + 3)^5 \\
 &:= (6 - 9 + 5 + 6 + 88 - 3 + 6 - 9 + 3)^5 \\
 &:= (-6 + 9 + 5 - 6 + 88 + 3 + 6 - 9 + 3)^5 \\
 &:= (-6 + 9 + 5 - 6 + 88 - 3 - 6 + 9 + 3)^5 \\
 &:= (6 - 9 + 5 - 6 + 88 + 3 - 6 + 9 + 3)^5 \\
 &:= (-6 - 9 + 5 + 6 + 88 + 3 - 6 + 9 + 3)^5 \\
 &:= (-6 - 9 + 5 - 6 + 88 + 3 + 6 + 9 + 3)^5 \\
 &:= (6 - 9 + 5 + 6 + 8 + 83 + 6 - 9 - 3)^5 \\
 &:= (-6 + 9 + 5 - 6 + 8 + 83 - 6 + 9 - 3)^5 \\
 &:= (6 + 9 + 5 - 6 + 8 + 83 - 6 - 9 + 3)^5 \\
 &:= (-6 + 9 + 5 + 6 + 8 + 83 - 6 - 9 + 3)^5 \\
 &:= (-6 + 9 + 5 - 6 + 8 + 83 + 6 - 9 + 3)^5 \\
 &:= (6 - 9 + 5 - 6 + 8 + 83 - 6 + 9 + 3)^5 \\
 &:= (-6 - 9 + 5 + 6 + 8 + 83 - 6 + 9 + 3)^5 \\
 &:= (-6 - 9 + 5 - 6 + 8 + 83 + 6 + 9 + 3)^5 \\
 &:= (6 + 9 + 5 - 6 + 8 + 8 - 3 + 69 - 3)^5 \\
 &:= (-6 + 9 + 5 + 6 + 8 + 8 - 3 + 69 - 3)^5 \\
 &:= (6 - 9 + 5 + 6 + 8 + 8 + 3 + 69 - 3)^5
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 &:= (6 - 9 + 5 + 6 + 8 + 8 - 3 + 69 + 3)^5 \\
 &:= (-6 + 9 + 5 - 6 + 8 + 8 + 3 + 69 + 3)^5 \\
 &:= (6 + 95 + 6 + 8 + 8 - 36 + 9 - 3)^5 \\
 &:= (6 - 9 + 56 + 8 + 8 + 36 - 9 - 3)^5 \\
 &:= (69 + 56 + 8 + 8 - 36 - 9 - 3)^5 \\
 &:= (-69 + 56 + 8 + 8 + 3 - 6 + 93)^5 \\
 &:= (69 - 56 - 8 - 8 - 3 + 6 + 93)^5 \\
 &:= (-69 + 5 + 68 + 83 - 6 + 9 + 3)^5 \\
 &:= (69 + 5 + 6 + 88 - 3 - 69 - 3)^5 \\
 &:= (-69 + 5 + 6 + 88 - 3 + 69 - 3)^5 \\
 &:= (69 + 5 - 6 + 88 + 3 - 69 + 3)^5 \\
 &:= (-69 + 5 - 6 + 88 + 3 + 69 + 3)^5 \\
 &:= (69 + 5 - 6 + 8 + 83 - 69 + 3)^5 \\
 &:= (-69 + 5 - 6 + 8 + 83 + 69 + 3)^5 \\
 &:= (6 + 95 + 68 + 8 + 3 + 6 - 93)^5 \\
 &:= (6 + 95 + 6 + 88 - 3 - 6 - 93)^5 \\
 &:= (6 + 95 - 6 + 88 - 3 + 6 - 93)^5 \\
 &:= (-6 + 95 + 6 + 88 - 3 + 6 - 93)^5 \\
 &:= (6 - 9 + 56 + 88 - 36 - 9 - 3)^5 \\
 &:= (-6 + 9 + 5 + 68 + 83 - 69 + 3)^5 \\
 &:= (69 + 5 + 68 + 8 + 36 - 93)^5 \\
 &:= (695 + 6 + 88 - 3 - 693)^5 \\
 &:= (6 + 95 + 688 - 3 - 693)^5 \\
 &:= (6 + 956 + 932 + 4 + 2 + 9)^3 \\
 &:= (6 + 9 + 7 - 5 + 7 - 5 + 7 - 4 - 4 - 1)^8 \\
 &:= (6 + 9 + 7 + 5 - 7 + 5 - 7 + 4 - 4 - 1)^8 \\
 &:= (6 + 9 - 7 + 5 + 7 + 5 - 7 + 4 - 4 - 1)^8 \\
 &:= (6 - 9 + 7 + 5 + 7 - 5 + 7 + 4 - 4 - 1)^8 \\
 &:= (6 + 9 - 7 + 5 - 7 + 5 + 7 + 4 - 4 - 1)^8 \\
 &:= (6 - 9 + 7 - 5 + 7 + 5 + 7 + 4 - 4 - 1)^8 \\
 &:= (6 + 9 + 7 + 5 - 7 + 5 - 7 - 4 + 4 - 1)^8 \\
 &:= (6 + 9 - 7 + 5 + 7 + 5 - 7 - 4 + 4 - 1)^8 \\
 &:= (6 - 9 + 7 + 5 + 7 - 5 + 7 - 4 + 4 - 1)^8 \\
 &:= (6 + 9 - 7 + 5 - 7 + 5 + 7 - 4 + 4 - 1)^8 \\
 &:= (6 - 9 + 7 - 5 + 7 + 5 + 7 - 4 + 4 - 1)^8 \\
 &:= (-6 + 9 + 7 + 5 + 7 - 5 - 7 + 4 + 4 - 1)^8 \\
 &:= (-6 + 9 + 7 - 5 + 7 + 5 - 7 + 4 + 4 - 1)^8 \\
 &:= (-6 + 9 + 7 + 5 - 7 - 5 + 7 + 4 + 4 - 1)^8
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} & := (-6+9-7+5+7-5+7+4+4-1)^8 & := (6+97-5-7+5-74-4-1)^8 \\ & := (-6+9+7-5-7+5+7+4+4-1)^8 & := (-6+97-5+7-5-74+4-1)^8 \\ & := (-6+9-7-5+7+5+7+4+4-1)^8 & := (-6+97+5-7+5-74-4+1)^8 \\ & := (-6+9+7+5+7-5+7-4-4+1)^8 & := (6+97-5-7-5-74+4+1)^8 \\ & := (-6+9+7-5+7+5+7-4-4+1)^8 & := (-6+9+75-75+7+4+4-1)^8 \\ & := (-6-9+7+5+7+5+7+4-4+1)^8 & := (-6+9-75+75+7+4+4-1)^8 \\ & := (-6-9+7+5+7+5+7-4+4+1)^8 & := (6+9+75-75-7+4+4+1)^8 \\ & := (6+9+7+5-7-5-7+4+4+1)^8 & := (6+9-75+75-7+4+4+1)^8 \\ & := (6+9-7+5+7-5-7+4+4+1)^8 & := (6+9+75-7-57-4-4-1)^8 \\ & := (6+9+7-5-7+5-7+4+4+1)^8 & := (-6-9+75+7-57+4+4-1)^8 \\ & := (6+9-7-5+7+5-7+4+4+1)^8 & := (6-9+75-7-57+4+4+1)^8 \\ & := (6+9-7+5-7-5+7+4+4+1)^8 & := (6+9+75-7+5-74+4-1)^8 \\ & := (6-9+7-5+7-5+7+4+4+1)^8 & := (-6+9-75+7+5+74+4-1)^8 \\ & := (6+9-7-5-7+5+7+4+4+1)^8 & := (6+9-75-7+5+74+4+1)^8 \\ & := (-6-9-7+5-7+5-7+44-1)^8 & := (-6+9+7+57-57+4+4-1)^8 \\ & := (-6+9-7-5-7-5-7+44+1)^8 & := (-6+9+7-57+57+4+4-1)^8 \\ & := (6-9+7-5-7-5-7-4+41)^8 & := (6+9-7+57-57+4+4+1)^8 \\ & := (6-9-7-5+7-5-7-4+41)^8 & := (6+9-7-57+57+4+4+1)^8 \\ & := (6-9-7-5-7-5+7-4+41)^8 & := (-6+9+7-57-5+74-4-1)^8 \\ & := (-6+9-7-5-7-5-7+4+41)^8 & := (-6-9+7-57+5+74+4-1)^8 \\ & := (69+7+5-7-5-7-44-1)^8 & := (6+9-7-57-5+74-4+1)^8 \\ & := (69-7+5+7-5-7-44-1)^8 & := (6-9-7-57+5+74+4+1)^8 \\ & := (69+7-5-7+5-7-44-1)^8 & := (6+9-7+5+75-74+4-1)^8 \\ & := (69-7-5+7+5-7-44-1)^8 & := (-6+9+7+5-75+74+4-1)^8 \\ & := (69-7+5-7-5+7-44-1)^8 & := (6+9-7+5-75+74+4+1)^8 \\ & := (69-7-5-7+5+7-44-1)^8 & := (-6-97-5+75+7+44-1)^8 \\ & := (69+7+5-7-5-7-4-41)^8 & := (6-97-5+75-7+44+1)^8 \\ & := (69-7+5+7-5-7-4-41)^8 & := (6-97-5+75-7+4+41)^8 \\ & := (69+7-5-7+5-7-4-41)^8 & := (6-97+5-7-5+74+41)^8 \\ & := (69-7-5+7+5-7-4-41)^8 & := (6-97-5-7+5+74+41)^8 \\ & := (69-7+5-7-5+7-4-41)^8 & := (-6-9-75+7+57+44-1)^8 \\ & := (69-7-5-7+5+7-4-41)^8 & := (6-9-75-7+57+44+1)^8 \\ & := (6+97+5-75-7-4-4-1)^8 & := (6-9-75-7+57+4+41)^8 \\ & := (-6+97-5-75+7+4-4-1)^8 & := (69+75-75-7-44-1)^8 \\ & := (-6+97-5-75+7-4+4-1)^8 & := (69-75+75-7-44-1)^8 \\ & := (6+97-5-75-7+4-4+1)^8 & := (69+75-75-7-4-41)^8 \\ & := (6+97-5-75-7-4+4+1)^8 & := (69-75+75-7-4-41)^8 \\ & := (6+97+5-7-5-74-4-1)^8 & := (69+75-7-5-74-41)^8 \end{aligned}$$

$:= (69 - 7 + 57 - 57 - 44 - 1)^8$	$:= (7 - 25 + 63 - 1 + 3 + 8 - 5 - 6)^6$
$:= (69 - 7 - 57 + 57 - 44 - 1)^8$	$:= (-7 - 25 + 63 + 1 + 3 + 8 - 5 + 6)^6$
$:= (69 - 7 + 57 - 57 - 4 - 41)^8$	$:= (7 - 25 + 63 - 1 - 3 - 8 + 5 + 6)^6$
$:= (69 - 7 - 57 + 57 - 4 - 41)^8$	$:= (7 + 2 + 56 - 31 + 3 + 8 + 5 - 6)^6$
$:= (69 - 7 - 5 + 75 - 74 - 41)^8$	$:= (-7 - 2 + 56 + 3 + 13 - 8 - 5 - 6)^6$
$:= (-6 - 9 + 757 - 5 - 7 - 441)^4$	$:= (-7 - 2 + 56 + 3 - 13 + 8 + 5 - 6)^6$
$:= (-6 - 9 - 7 - 5 + 757 - 441)^4$	$:= (7 - 2 + 56 + 3 - 13 - 8 - 5 + 6)^6$
6978430369 $:= (-697 + 84303 - 69)^2$	$:= (-7 + 2 + 56 - 3 - 13 + 8 - 5 + 6)^6$
6978821031 $:= (-6 - 97 - 88 + 2103 - 1)^3$	$:= (-7 + 2 + 56 + 3 - 13 - 8 + 5 + 6)^6$
6985783561 $:= (69 + 8 - 57 + 83561)^2$	$:= (7 + 2 + 5 - 63 - 1 + 3 + 85 + 6)^6$
7055792632 $:= (705 + 579 + 2 + 632)^3$	$:= (7 + 2 + 5 - 6 - 31 + 3 + 8 + 56)^6$
7056840025 $:= (7 - 05 + 6 + 84002 - 5)^2$	$:= (7 - 2 - 5 + 6 + 3 - 13 - 8 + 56)^6$
7058184169 $:= (-70 - 5 - 81 + 84169)^2$	$:= (-7 + 2 + 5 + 6 + 3 - 13 - 8 + 56)^6$
7114585104 $:= (-711 - 45 + 85104)^2$	$:= (-7 - 2 - 5 - 6 + 3 + 13 - 8 + 56)^6$
7119984400 $:= (7 + 1 - 19 - 9 + 84400)^2$	$:= (-7 + 2 - 5 + 6 - 3 - 13 + 8 + 56)^6$
7184766169 $:= (-71 + 84766 - 1 + 69)^2$	$:= (-7 - 2 + 5 - 6 + 3 - 13 + 8 + 56)^6$
7225850025 $:= (7 - 2 - 2 + 5 + 85002 - 5)^2$	$:= (72 + 56 + 3 + 1 + 3 - 85 - 6)^6$
$:= (7 - 2 - 2 - 5 + 85002 + 5)^2$	$:= (72 + 56 - 3 + 1 - 3 - 85 + 6)^6$
$:= (-7 + 2 - 2 + 5 + 85002 + 5)^2$	$:= (72 - 5 - 63 + 1 + 38 - 5 + 6)^6$
$:= (-7 - 2 + 2 + 5 + 85002 + 5)^2$	$:= (-72 + 5 + 63 - 1 + 38 + 5 + 6)^6$
7256313856 $:= (7 + 2 + 5 + 6 + 3 - 1 + 3 + 8 + 5 + 6)^6$	$:= (7 + 25 - 63 - 1 - 3 + 85 - 6)^6$
$:= (7 + 25 + 6 + 3 - 1 - 3 + 8 + 5 - 6)^6$	$:= (-7 + 25 - 63 + 1 - 3 + 85 + 6)^6$
$:= (7 + 25 + 6 - 3 - 1 + 3 + 8 + 5 - 6)^6$	$:= (7 + 25 + 6 - 31 + 38 + 5 - 6)^6$
$:= (7 + 25 - 6 + 3 - 1 - 3 + 8 + 5 + 6)^6$	$:= (7 - 25 - 6 + 31 + 38 + 5 - 6)^6$
$:= (-7 + 25 + 6 + 3 + 1 - 3 + 8 + 5 + 6)^6$	$:= (-7 - 25 + 6 + 31 + 38 - 5 + 6)^6$
$:= (7 + 25 - 6 - 3 - 1 + 3 + 8 + 5 + 6)^6$	$:= (7 + 25 - 6 - 31 + 38 + 5 + 6)^6$
$:= (-7 + 25 + 6 - 3 + 1 + 3 + 8 + 5 + 6)^6$	$:= (-7 + 25 + 6 - 31 + 3 - 8 + 56)^6$
$:= (7 + 2 - 5 + 63 - 1 - 3 - 8 - 5 - 6)^6$	$:= (-7 - 25 - 6 + 31 + 3 - 8 + 56)^6$
$:= (-7 - 2 + 5 + 63 + 1 + 3 - 8 - 5 - 6)^6$	$:= (-7 + 25 - 6 - 3 - 13 - 8 + 56)^6$
$:= (-7 - 2 - 5 + 63 + 1 - 3 + 8 - 5 - 6)^6$	$:= (-7 + 25 + 6 + 3 - 1 - 38 + 56)^6$
$:= (-7 - 2 - 5 + 63 + 1 + 3 - 8 + 5 - 6)^6$	$:= (7 - 2 - 56 + 3 + 13 + 85 - 6)^6$
$:= (-7 + 2 - 5 + 63 + 1 - 3 - 8 - 5 + 6)^6$	$:= (7 - 2 - 5 + 63 - 1 + 38 - 56)^6$
$:= (-7 - 2 - 5 + 63 - 1 + 3 - 8 - 5 + 6)^6$	$:= (-7 + 2 + 5 + 63 - 1 + 38 - 56)^6$
$:= (72 + 5 - 6 - 31 - 3 + 8 + 5 - 6)^6$	$:= (7 + 2 + 5 - 63 - 1 + 38 + 56)^6$
$:= (72 - 5 + 6 + 3 - 13 - 8 - 5 - 6)^6$	$:= (-7 - 25 - 63 + 138 - 5 + 6)^6$
$:= (72 - 5 - 6 + 3 - 13 - 8 - 5 + 6)^6$	$:= (7 + 25 + 63 + 13 - 8 - 56)^6$
$:= (72 + 5 + 6 - 3 + 1 - 38 - 5 + 6)^6$	7261084944 $:= (7 + 261 + 084944)^2$
$:= (72 - 5 + 6 - 3 + 1 - 38 + 5 + 6)^6$	7268585536 $:= (-7 - 268 - 5 + 85536)^2$

$$\begin{aligned}
 \mathbf{7269949696} &:= (72 + 6 + 99 + 4 + 96 + 9 + 6)^4 \\
 &:= (72 + 6 + 99 + 4 + 9 + 6 + 96)^4 \\
 &:= (72 + 6 + 9 + 94 + 96 + 9 + 6)^4 \\
 &:= (72 + 6 + 9 + 94 + 9 + 6 + 96)^4 \\
 &:= (72 + 6 + 9 + 9 + 4 + 96 + 96)^4 \\
 &:= (-7 - 2 + 6 + 99 + 4 + 96 + 96)^4 \\
 &:= (7 + 2 + 6 - 9 + 94 + 96 + 96)^4 \\
 &:= (-7 - 2 + 6 + 9 + 94 + 96 + 96)^4 \\
 &:= (7 + 2 - 6 + 994 - 9 - 696)^4 \\
 &:= (-7 - 2 - 6 + 994 + 9 - 696)^4
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 \mathbf{7339040224} &:= (73 + 39 + 04 + 02 - 24)^5 \\
 &:= (7 + 33 + 90 - 40 + 2 - 2 + 4)^5 \\
 &:= (-7 - 33 + 90 + 40 + 2 - 2 + 4)^5 \\
 &:= (7 + 33 + 90 - 40 - 2 + 2 + 4)^5 \\
 &:= (-7 - 33 + 90 + 40 - 2 + 2 + 4)^5 \\
 &:= (-7 + 33 + 90 + 4 - 022 - 4)^5 \\
 &:= (-7 + 33 + 90 - 4 - 022 + 4)^5 \\
 &:= (7 - 33 + 90 + 4 + 022 + 4)^5 \\
 &:= (-7 + 33 + 90 + 4 - 02 - 24)^5 \\
 &:= (7 - 33 + 90 + 4 + 02 + 24)^5 \\
 &:= (73 + 39 - 040 - 2 + 24)^5 \\
 &:= (73 - 3 + 90 - 40 - 22 - 4)^5 \\
 &:= (73 - 3 + 90 - 40 - 2 - 24)^5 \\
 &:= (-7 + 33 + 90 - 40 + 22 - 4)^5 \\
 &:= (7 - 339 + 0402 + 24)^5
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\mathbf{7370050801} := (7 + 370 - 05 - 080 + 1)^4$$

$$\mathbf{7374859129} := (7 - 37 + 4 + 85912 - 9)^2$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 \mathbf{7385855481} &:= (73 + 85855 + 4 + 8 + 1)^2 \\
 &:= (7 + 385 + 85548 + 1)^2
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\mathbf{7392083392} := (-7 - 39 + 2083 + 3 - 92)^3$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 \mathbf{7471182096} &:= (74 + 7 + 1 + 1 + 8 + 209 - 6)^4 \\
 &:= (7 + 4 + 71 + 1 + 8 + 209 - 6)^4
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 \mathbf{7488652369} &:= (7 - 4 + 8 + 86523 - 6 + 9)^2 \\
 &:= (-7 - 48 + 86523 + 69)^2
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\mathbf{7524868516} := (-75 - 24 + 86851 - 6)^2$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 \mathbf{7547786884} &:= (7 + 5 - 4 - 7 - 7 + 86884)^2 \\
 &:= (-7 + 5 - 4 + 7 - 7 + 86884)^2 \\
 &:= (-7 + 5 - 4 - 7 + 7 + 86884)^2
 \end{aligned}$$

$$:= (75 - 4 - 77 + 86884)^2$$

$$\mathbf{7573350625} := (-7 + 5 - 7 + 335 - 06 - 25)^4$$

$$:= (7 - 5 + 7 + 3 + 350 - 62 - 5)^4$$

$$:= (7 + 5 - 7 - 3 + 350 - 62 + 5)^4$$

$$:= (-7 + 5 + 7 - 3 + 350 - 62 + 5)^4$$

$$:= (7 + 5 - 7 - 335 + 0625)^4$$

$$:= (-7 + 5 + 7 - 335 + 0625)^4$$

$$:= (75 + 733 - 506 - 2 - 5)^4$$

$$:= (75 - 73 + 350 - 62 + 5)^4$$

$$\mathbf{7608723984} := (7 - 6 + 087239 - 8 - 4)^2$$

$$\mathbf{7651875625} := (-76 - 5 - 1 + 87562 - 5)^2$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 \mathbf{7658875225} &:= (7 - 6 + 5 - 8 + 87522 - 5)^2 \\
 &:= (7 - 6 - 5 - 8 + 87522 + 5)^2
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\mathbf{7668680041} := (766 + 86800 + 4 + 1)^2$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 \mathbf{7668682048} &:= (-76 + 6 + 8 - 6 - 8 + 2048)^3 \\
 &:= (-76 - 6 + 8 + 6 - 8 + 2048)^3
 \end{aligned}$$

$$:= (-76 + 6 - 8 - 6 + 8 + 2048)^3$$

$$:= (-76 - 6 - 8 + 6 + 8 + 2048)^3$$

$$:= (-76 + 68 - 68 + 2048)^3$$

$$:= (-76 - 68 + 68 + 2048)^3$$

$$\mathbf{7676563456} := (7 - 67 + 6 + 5 + 6 + 345 - 6)^4$$

$$:= (7 - 67 + 6 + 5 - 6 + 345 + 6)^4$$

$$:= (7 - 67 - 6 + 5 + 6 + 345 + 6)^4$$

$$:= (-76 - 76 - 5 - 6 + 3 + 456)^4$$

$$:= (-76 + 765 + 63 - 456)^4$$

$$\mathbf{7692038424} := (7 - 69 + 2038 + 4 - 2 - 4)^3$$

$$:= (7 - 69 + 2038 - 4 - 2 + 4)^3$$

$$\mathbf{7727161833} := (77 + 2 + 71 - 6 + 1833)^3$$

$$:= (7 + 72 + 71 - 6 + 1833)^3$$

$$\mathbf{7737809375} := (77 + 3 + 7 + 8 + 09 + 3 - 7 - 5)^5$$

$$:= (77 + 3 - 7 + 8 + 09 + 3 + 7 - 5)^5$$

$$:= (77 + 3 + 7 + 8 - 09 - 3 + 7 + 5)^5$$

$$:= (77 - 3 + 7 + 8 - 09 + 3 + 7 + 5)^5$$

$$:= (7 + 73 + 7 + 8 + 09 + 3 - 7 - 5)^5$$

$$:= (7 + 73 - 7 + 8 + 09 + 3 + 7 - 5)^5$$

$$:= (-7 + 73 + 7 + 8 + 09 + 3 + 7 - 5)^5$$

$$:= (7 + 73 + 7 + 8 - 09 - 3 + 7 + 5)^5$$

$$:= (7 + 7 + 3 + 78 + 09 + 3 - 7 - 5)^5$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 &:= (7 - 7 + 3 + 78 + 09 + 3 + 7 - 5)^5 \\
 &:= (-7 + 7 + 3 + 78 + 09 + 3 + 7 - 5)^5 \\
 &:= (7 + 7 + 3 + 78 - 09 - 3 + 7 + 5)^5 \\
 &:= (7 + 7 - 3 + 78 - 09 + 3 + 7 + 5)^5 \\
 &:= (7 - 7 + 3 - 7 + 8 + 093 - 7 + 5)^5 \\
 &:= (-7 + 7 + 3 - 7 + 8 + 093 - 7 + 5)^5 \\
 &:= (-7 - 7 + 3 + 7 + 8 + 093 - 7 + 5)^5 \\
 &:= (-7 - 7 + 3 - 7 + 8 + 093 + 7 + 5)^5 \\
 &:= (7 + 7 + 3 + 7 + 8 - 09 - 3 + 75)^5 \\
 &:= (7 + 7 - 3 + 7 + 8 - 09 + 3 + 75)^5 \\
 &:= (-7 - 7 + 37 + 80 - 9 + 3 - 7 + 5)^5 \\
 &:= (-7 - 7 + 3 - 7 + 80 - 9 + 37 + 5)^5 \\
 &:= (77 - 37 - 8 - 09 - 3 + 75)^5 \\
 &:= (-77 + 3 + 78 + 093 - 7 + 5)^5 \\
 &:= (77 + 3 + 78 + 09 + 3 - 75)^5 \\
 &:= (-77 + 3 - 7 + 8 + 093 + 75)^5 \\
 &:= (7 + 73 + 78 + 09 + 3 - 75)^5 \\
 \mathbf{7744880025} &:= (7 - 7 + 4 + 4 + 88002 - 5)^2 \\
 &:= (-7 + 7 + 4 + 4 + 88002 - 5)^2 \\
 \mathbf{7762392000} &:= (7 - 7 - 6 - 2 - 3 - 9 + 2000)^3 \\
 &:= (-7 + 7 - 6 - 2 - 3 - 9 + 2000)^3 \\
 &:= (7 - 7 - 6 - 23 + 9 + 2000)^3 \\
 &:= (-7 + 7 - 6 - 23 + 9 + 2000)^3 \\
 \mathbf{7780827681} &:= (7 + 7 + 8 + 08 + 276 - 8 - 1)^4 \\
 &:= (7 + 7 + 8 - 08 + 276 + 8 - 1)^4 \\
 &:= (7 + 7 - 8 + 08 + 276 + 8 - 1)^4 \\
 &:= (7 + 7 + 80 + 8 + 276 - 81)^4 \\
 \mathbf{7798832721} &:= (7 + 7 - 9 + 88327 - 21)^2 \\
 \mathbf{7809531904} &:= (7 + 80 - 9 + 5 - 3 + 1904)^3 \\
 &:= (-7 + 80 + 9 - 5 + 3 + 1904)^3 \\
 \mathbf{7859886336} &:= (7 + 8 + 5 + 9 + 88633 - 6)^2 \\
 \mathbf{7879757824} &:= (7 + 87975 + 782 + 4)^2 \\
 \mathbf{7886150416} &:= (788 + 6 + 1 - 504 + 1 + 6)^4 \\
 &:= (7 + 88 + 6 + 150 + 41 + 6)^4 \\
 &:= (7 + 8 + 86 + 150 + 41 + 6)^4 \\
 &:= (-7 + 8 - 8 - 61 - 50 + 416)^4 \\
 &:= (-7 - 8 + 8 - 61 - 50 + 416)^4 \\
 \mathbf{7887571344} &:= (7 + 88757 + 1 + 3 + 44)^2 \\
 \mathbf{7887748969} &:= (7 + 88774 + 8 + 9 + 6 + 9)^2 \\
 \mathbf{7888281856} &:= (7 + 88828 - 18 + 5 - 6)^2 \\
 \mathbf{7964053973} &:= (7 + 964 + 053 + 973)^3 \\
 \mathbf{7976023992} &:= (7 + 976 + 023 + 992)^3 \\
 \mathbf{7988005999} &:= (7 + 988 + 005 + 999)^3 \\
 \mathbf{7992538801} &:= (-7 - 9 - 9 + 253 - 8 + 80 - 1)^4 \\
 \mathbf{8024024008} &:= (8 + 02402 - 400 - 8)^3 \\
 &:= (-8 + 02402 - 400 + 8)^3 \\
 \mathbf{8031810176} &:= (-8 + 031 - 8 - 1 - 01 + 7 + 6)^7 \\
 &:= (8 - 03 + 18 + 1 + 01 + 7 - 6)^7 \\
 &:= (8 + 03 + 18 - 1 - 01 - 7 + 6)^7 \\
 &:= (-8 + 03 + 18 + 1 - 01 + 7 + 6)^7 \\
 &:= (-8 + 03 + 18 - 1 + 01 + 7 + 6)^7 \\
 &:= (8 - 03 + 1 + 8 + 10 + 1 + 7 - 6)^7 \\
 &:= (8 + 03 - 1 + 8 + 10 - 1 - 7 + 6)^7 \\
 &:= (8 + 03 + 1 - 8 + 10 - 1 + 7 + 6)^7 \\
 &:= (-8 + 03 + 1 + 8 + 10 - 1 + 7 + 6)^7 \\
 &:= (8 + 03 - 1 - 8 + 10 + 1 + 7 + 6)^7 \\
 &:= (-8 + 03 - 1 + 8 + 10 + 1 + 7 + 6)^7 \\
 &:= (8 - 03 + 1 + 8 + 1 + 017 - 6)^7 \\
 &:= (8 + 03 + 1 - 8 - 1 + 017 + 6)^7 \\
 &:= (-8 + 03 + 1 + 8 - 1 + 017 + 6)^7 \\
 &:= (8 + 03 - 1 - 8 + 1 + 017 + 6)^7 \\
 &:= (-8 + 03 - 1 + 8 + 1 + 017 + 6)^7 \\
 &:= (80 - 31 - 8 - 1 - 01 - 7 - 6)^7 \\
 &:= (80 + 3 + 1 - 81 + 017 + 6)^7 \\
 &:= (-80 + 3 - 1 + 81 + 017 + 6)^7 \\
 &:= (-80 - 3 - 1 + 8 + 101 + 7 - 6)^7 \\
 &:= (-80 - 3 + 1 + 8 + 101 - 7 + 6)^7 \\
 &:= (8 + 031 + 8 - 10 - 17 + 6)^7 \\
 &:= (-8 + 03 + 18 - 10 + 17 + 6)^7 \\
 &:= (8 + 03 - 18 + 10 + 17 + 6)^7 \\
 &:= (-80 + 31 + 8 - 10 + 1 + 76)^7 \\
 &:= (80 - 3 - 18 - 10 - 17 - 6)^7 \\
 &:= (-80 + 3 + 18 + 10 - 1 + 76)^7 \\
 \mathbf{8033895424} &:= (80 + 3 + 3 + 89542 + 4)^2 \\
 \mathbf{8068889929} &:= (-80 - 6 - 8 - 8 + 89929)^2 \\
 &:= (-8 - 06 - 88 + 89929)^2
 \end{aligned}$$

8100900025 := (8 - 10 + 090002 + 5) ²	:= (81 + 5 - 3 - 72 - 6 + 97 - 6) ⁵
8118190201 := (-81 - 18 - 1 + 90201) ²	:= (-81 + 5 + 3 + 72 + 6 + 97 - 6) ⁵
:= (-8 - 11 - 81 + 90201) ²	:= (-81 + 5 + 3 + 72 - 6 + 97 + 6) ⁵
:= (81 - 181 + 90201) ²	:= (81 + 5 + 3 - 72 - 6 + 9 + 76) ⁵
8153726976 := (81 + 5 + 3 + 7 - 2 + 6 + 9 - 7 - 6) ⁵	:= (8 + 153 + 7 - 2 - 69 - 7 + 6) ⁵
:= (81 + 5 + 3 + 7 + 2 + 6 - 9 + 7 - 6) ⁵	:= (8 + 153 - 7 - 2 - 69 + 7 + 6) ⁵
:= (81 + 5 - 3 + 7 + 2 - 6 + 9 + 7 - 6) ⁵	:= (8 + 15 + 37 + 26 + 9 + 7 - 6) ⁵
:= (81 + 5 + 3 - 7 - 2 + 6 + 9 + 7 - 6) ⁵	:= (8 - 15 + 37 - 2 + 69 - 7 + 6) ⁵
:= (81 + 5 + 3 + 7 - 2 - 6 + 9 - 7 + 6) ⁵	:= (8 + 15 + 3 - 7 - 26 + 97 + 6) ⁵
:= (81 - 5 - 3 + 7 + 2 + 6 + 9 - 7 + 6) ⁵	:= (-8 - 15 - 3 - 7 + 26 + 97 + 6) ⁵
:= (81 + 5 + 3 + 7 + 2 - 6 - 9 + 7 + 6) ⁵	:= (-8 + 15 + 3 - 7 + 26 - 9 + 76) ⁵
:= (81 + 5 + 3 - 7 - 2 - 6 + 9 + 7 + 6) ⁵	:= (8 - 15 + 3 + 7 + 26 - 9 + 76) ⁵
:= (81 - 5 - 3 - 7 + 2 + 6 + 9 + 7 + 6) ⁵	:= (8 - 1 - 53 + 72 + 69 + 7 - 6) ⁵
:= (8 + 1 + 5 + 3 + 7 + 2 + 69 + 7 - 6) ⁵	:= (8 + 1 - 53 + 72 + 69 - 7 + 6) ⁵
:= (8 - 1 + 5 - 3 + 7 - 2 + 69 + 7 + 6) ⁵	:= (8 + 1 + 53 - 7 - 26 - 9 + 76) ⁵
:= (8 - 1 - 5 + 3 + 7 + 2 + 69 + 7 + 6) ⁵	:= (-8 - 1 + 53 - 7 - 26 + 9 + 76) ⁵
:= (81 - 5 - 3 + 7 + 26 - 9 - 7 + 6) ⁵	:= (8 + 1 - 53 - 7 + 2 + 69 + 76) ⁵
:= (81 - 5 - 3 - 7 + 26 - 9 + 7 + 6) ⁵	:= (8 + 1 - 5 - 37 + 26 + 97 + 6) ⁵
:= (8 + 15 + 3 + 72 + 6 - 9 + 7 - 6) ⁵	:= (-8 - 1 - 5 - 37 + 2 + 69 + 76) ⁵
:= (8 + 15 - 3 + 72 - 6 + 9 + 7 - 6) ⁵	:= (8 + 1 + 5 + 3 + 72 - 69 + 76) ⁵
:= (-8 + 15 + 3 + 72 + 6 + 9 - 7 + 6) ⁵	:= (815 - 3 - 726 + 9 + 7 - 6) ⁵
:= (8 + 15 + 3 + 72 - 6 - 9 + 7 + 6) ⁵	:= (815 + 3 - 726 - 9 + 7 + 6) ⁵
:= (8 - 15 + 3 + 72 + 6 + 9 + 7 + 6) ⁵	:= (-81 + 53 + 7 + 26 + 97 - 6) ⁵
:= (8 + 15 - 3 - 7 - 2 - 6 + 97 - 6) ⁵	:= (8 + 153 - 72 - 69 + 76) ⁵
:= (-8 + 15 - 3 - 7 + 2 + 6 + 97 - 6) ⁵	
:= (8 - 15 - 3 + 7 + 2 + 6 + 97 - 6) ⁵	
:= (-8 + 15 - 3 - 7 + 2 - 6 + 97 + 6) ⁵	
:= (8 - 15 - 3 + 7 + 2 - 6 + 97 + 6) ⁵	
:= (8 - 15 + 3 - 7 - 2 + 6 + 97 + 6) ⁵	
:= (8 + 15 + 3 + 7 + 2 - 6 - 9 + 76) ⁵	
:= (8 + 15 + 3 - 7 - 2 - 6 + 9 + 76) ⁵	
:= (-8 + 15 + 3 - 7 + 2 + 6 + 9 + 76) ⁵	
:= (8 - 15 + 3 + 7 + 2 + 6 + 9 + 76) ⁵	
:= (-8 - 1 + 53 - 7 - 2 - 6 - 9 + 76) ⁵	
:= (-8 - 1 + 5 + 37 + 2 - 6 - 9 + 76) ⁵	
:= (-8 + 1 - 5 + 37 - 2 + 6 - 9 + 76) ⁵	
:= (81 - 53 + 72 + 6 - 9 - 7 + 6) ⁵	
:= (81 - 53 - 7 + 2 + 6 - 9 + 76) ⁵	
	8208541201 := (82 + 08 + 5 + 4 + 1 + 201) ⁴
	:= (8 + 2 + 085 + 4 + 1 + 201) ⁴
	:= (-8 + 20 + 85 + 4 - 1 + 201) ⁴
	8230172859 := (-823 - 017 + 2859) ³
	8248090761 := (8 + 2 + 48 + 090761) ²
	8263900836 := (826 + 3 + 90083 - 6) ²
	8279186167 := (82 + 79 + 1861 - 6 + 7) ³
	8303765625 := (8 + 3 + 03 + 7 + 6 + 5 + 6 + 2 + 5) ⁶
	:= (-8 - 3 - 03 + 7 + 65 - 6 - 2 - 5) ⁶
	:= (-8 - 3 - 03 - 7 + 65 - 6 + 2 + 5) ⁶
	:= (-8 + 3 - 03 + 7 - 6 - 5 + 62 - 5) ⁶
	:= (-8 - 3 + 03 + 7 - 6 - 5 + 62 - 5) ⁶
	:= (-8 - 3 - 03 - 7 - 6 + 5 + 62 + 5) ⁶
	:= (8 + 3 - 03 + 7 + 6 + 5 - 6 + 25) ⁶

$$\begin{aligned}
 & := (8 - 3 + 03 + 7 + 6 + 5 - 6 + 25)^6 & & := (-84 - 2 - 8 + 8 - 92 + 481)^4 \\
 & := (8 + 3 - 03 + 7 - 6 + 5 + 6 + 25)^6 & & := (8 + 428 + 8 - 92 - 48 - 1)^4 \\
 & := (8 - 3 + 03 + 7 - 6 + 5 + 6 + 25)^6 & & := (8 - 4 - 2 - 88 - 92 + 481)^4 \\
 & := (83 - 03 + 7 - 6 - 5 - 6 - 25)^6 & & \mathbf{8464920025} := (-8 + 4 + 6 - 4 + 92002 + 5)^2 \\
 & := (-8 + 30 + 37 - 6 + 5 - 6 - 2 - 5)^6 & & := (-8 - 4 + 6 + 4 + 92002 + 5)^2 \\
 & := (-8 + 30 + 37 - 6 - 5 - 6 - 2 + 5)^6 & & \mathbf{8539238464} := (85 + 3 + 92384 - 64)^2 \\
 & := (8 - 30 - 3 + 76 - 5 + 6 - 2 - 5)^6 & & \mathbf{8540717056} := (-85 + 407 - 17 + 05 - 6)^4 \\
 & := (-8 - 30 + 3 + 76 + 5 + 6 - 2 - 5)^6 & & := (8 + 5 - 407 - 1 + 705 - 6)^4 \\
 & := (-8 - 30 + 3 + 76 - 5 + 6 - 2 + 5)^6 & & \mathbf{8577357823} := (-8 - 5773 + 5 + 7823)^3 \\
 & := (8 - 30 + 3 + 7 - 6 + 56 + 2 + 5)^6 & & \mathbf{8587340257} := (85 + 8 + 7 + 3 + 4 + 02 - 5 - 7)^5 \\
 & := (-8 + 3 - 03 + 7 + 65 + 6 - 25)^6 & & := (85 + 8 + 7 - 3 + 4 - 02 + 5 - 7)^5 \\
 & := (-8 - 3 + 03 + 7 + 65 + 6 - 25)^6 & & := (85 + 8 + 7 - 3 - 4 + 02 - 5 + 7)^5 \\
 & := (-83 + 03 + 76 + 56 - 2 - 5)^6 & & := (85 + 8 - 7 + 3 + 4 + 02 - 5 + 7)^5 \\
 & := (-83 + 03 - 7 + 65 + 62 + 5)^6 & & := (85 + 8 - 7 - 3 + 4 - 02 + 5 + 7)^5 \\
 & := (83 + 03 - 7 - 65 + 6 + 25)^6 & & := (85 - 8 + 7 + 3 - 4 + 02 + 5 + 7)^5 \\
 & := (-8 - 30 + 37 - 6 - 5 + 62 - 5)^6 & & := (8 + 5 + 87 + 3 + 4 + 02 - 5 - 7)^5 \\
 & := (8 + 30 + 37 + 6 - 5 - 6 - 25)^6 & & := (8 + 5 + 87 - 3 + 4 - 02 + 5 - 7)^5 \\
 & := (8 + 30 + 37 - 6 - 5 + 6 - 25)^6 & & := (8 - 5 + 87 + 3 + 4 + 02 + 5 - 7)^5 \\
 & := (8 - 30 + 37 + 6 + 5 - 6 + 25)^6 & & := (8 - 5 + 87 + 3 + 4 - 02 - 5 + 7)^5 \\
 & := (8 - 30 + 37 - 6 + 5 + 6 + 25)^6 & & := (8 + 5 + 87 - 3 - 4 + 02 - 5 + 7)^5 \\
 & := (8 + 30 + 3 + 76 - 5 - 62 - 5)^6 & & := (8 - 5 + 87 - 3 - 4 + 02 + 5 + 7)^5 \\
 & := (-8 - 30 + 3 - 7 + 6 + 56 + 25)^6 & & := (-8 + 5 + 87 + 3 - 4 + 02 + 5 + 7)^5 \\
 & := (-8 + 3 - 037 + 6 + 56 + 25)^6 & & := (85 - 8 - 7 - 3 + 40 + 2 - 5 - 7)^5 \\
 & := (83 + 037 + 6 - 56 - 25)^6 & & := (85 + 8 - 7 - 3 - 4 + 025 - 7)^5 \\
 & := (-8 - 30 + 37 + 65 + 6 - 25)^6 & & := (8 + 58 + 7 + 34 + 02 - 5 - 7)^5 \\
 \mathbf{8318169616} := (-8 + 318 - 16 + 9 + 6 - 1 - 6)^4 & & := (8 + 58 - 7 + 34 + 02 - 5 + 7)^5 \\
 & := (8 + 318 - 16 - 9 + 6 + 1 - 6)^4 & & := (-8 + 58 - 7 + 3 - 4 - 02 + 57)^5 \\
 & := (-8 + 318 - 16 + 9 - 6 - 1 + 6)^4 & & := (-8 - 5 + 87 - 3 + 40 - 2 - 5 - 7)^5 \\
 & := (8 + 318 - 16 - 9 - 6 + 1 + 6)^4 & & := (8 - 5 + 8 - 7 + 34 + 02 + 57)^5 \\
 & := (8 + 318 + 1 + 6 - 9 - 6 - 16)^4 & & := (8 + 5 + 8 + 7 - 3 + 40 + 25 + 7)^5 \\
 & := (-8 + 318 - 1 + 6 + 9 - 6 - 16)^4 & & := (85 + 8 - 7 + 3 + 40 - 25 - 7)^5 \\
 & := (8 + 318 + 1 - 6 - 9 + 6 - 16)^4 & & := (-8 + 58 + 73 - 40 + 2 + 5 + 7)^5 \\
 & := (-8 + 318 - 1 - 6 + 9 + 6 - 16)^4 & & := (8 + 5 - 8 + 73 - 40 + 2 + 57)^5 \\
 & := (8 - 318 - 1 + 6 - 9 + 616)^4 & & := (-8 + 5 + 8 + 73 - 40 + 2 + 57)^5 \\
 \mathbf{8329117696} := (83 + 2 + 91176 + 9 - 6)^2 & & := (85 + 87 - 3 - 40 - 25 - 7)^5 \\
 \mathbf{8377795791} := (8 - 3777 + 9 + 5791)^3 & & := (8 + 5 + 8 - 7 + 340 - 257)^5 \\
 \mathbf{8419163536} := (84 + 1 + 91635 + 36)^2 & & \mathbf{8589934592} := (8 + 5 - 8 + 9 + 9 - 3 + 4 - 5 - 9 - 2)^{11} \\
 \mathbf{8428892481} := (-84 - 2 + 8 - 8 - 92 + 481)^4 & & := (-8 + 5 + 8 + 9 + 9 - 3 + 4 - 5 - 9 - 2)^{11}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} &:= (8-5+8+9-9+3+4-5-9-2)^{33} &:= (8-5+8-9+9-3-4+5-9+2)^{33} \\ &:= (8-5+8-9+9+3+4-5-9-2)^{33} &:= (8+5-8+9-9+3-4+5-9+2)^{33} \\ &:= (8+5+8+9-9-3-4+5-9-2)^{11} &:= (8-5+8+9-9+3-4+5-9+2)^{11} \\ &:= (8+5+8-9+9-3-4+5-9-2)^{11} &:= (-8+5+8+9-9+3-4+5-9+2)^{33} \\ &:= (8-5-8+9+9-3+4+5-9-2)^{11} &:= (8+5-8-9+9+3-4+5-9+2)^{33} \\ &:= (-8+5-8+9+9-3+4+5-9-2)^{33} &:= (8-5+8-9+9+3-4+5-9+2)^{11} \\ &:= (-8-5+8+9+9-3+4+5-9-2)^{11} &:= (-8+5+8-9+9+3-4+5-9+2)^{33} \\ &:= (-8+5-8+9+9+3+4+5-9-2)^{11} &:= (8+5+8-9-9-3+4+5-9+2)^{33} \\ &:= (8-5-8+9+9-3-4-5+9-2)^{11} &:= (8+5+8-9-9+3+4+5-9+2)^{11} \\ &:= (-8+5-8+9+9-3-4-5+9-2)^{33} &:= (-8-5-8+9+9+3+4+5-9+2)^{33} \\ &:= (-8-5+8+9+9-3-4-5+9-2)^{11} &:= (8+5+8-9-9-3-4-5+9+2)^{33} \\ &:= (-8+5-8+9+9+3-4-5+9-2)^{11} &:= (8+5+8-9-9+3-4-5+9+2)^{11} \\ &:= (8+5-8+9-9-3+4-5+9-2)^{11} &:= (-8-5-8+9+9+3-4-5+9+2)^{33} \\ &:= (-8+5+8+9-9-3+4-5+9-2)^{11} &:= (8-5-8+9-9-3+4-5+9+2)^{33} \\ &:= (8+5-8-9+9-3+4-5+9-2)^{11} &:= (-8-5+8+9-9-3+4-5+9+2)^{33} \\ &:= (-8+5+8-9+9-3+4-5+9-2)^{11} &:= (8-5-8-9+9-3+4-5+9+2)^{33} \\ &:= (8-5+8-9-9+3+4-5+9-2)^{33} &:= (-8-5+8-9+9-3+4-5+9+2)^{33} \\ &:= (8+5+8-9-9-3-4+5+9-2)^{11} &:= (8-5-8+9-9+3+4-5+9+2)^{11} \\ &:= (-8-5-8+9+9-3-4+5+9-2)^{33} &:= (-8+5-8+9-9+3+4-5+9+2)^{33} \\ &:= (-8-5-8+9+9+3-4+5+9-2)^{11} &:= (-8-5+8+9-9+3+4-5+9+2)^{11} \\ &:= (8-5-8+9-9-3+4+5+9-2)^{11} &:= (8-5-8-9+9+3+4-5+9+2)^{11} \\ &:= (-8+5-8+9-9-3+4+5+9-2)^{33} &:= (-8+5-8-9+9+3+4-5+9+2)^{33} \\ &:= (-8-5+8+9-9-3+4+5+9-2)^{11} &:= (-8-5+8-9+9+3+4-5+9+2)^{11} \\ &:= (8-5-8-9+9-3+4+5+9-2)^{11} &:= (8-5+8-9-9-3-4+5+9+2)^{33} \\ &:= (-8+5-8-9+9-3+4+5+9-2)^{33} &:= (8+5-8-9-9+3-4+5+9+2)^{33} \\ &:= (-8-5+8-9+9-3+4+5+9-2)^{11} &:= (8-5+8-9-9+3-4+5+9+2)^{11} \\ &:= (-8+5-8+9-9+3+4+5+9-2)^{11} &:= (-8+5+8-9-9+3-4+5+9+2)^{33} \\ &:= (-8+5-8-9+9+3+4+5+9-2)^{11} &:= (-8-5-8+9-9+3+4+5+9+2)^{33} \\ &:= (8+5+8+9-9-3-4-5-9+2)^{33} &:= (-8-5-8-9+9+3+4+5+9+2)^{33} \\ &:= (8+5+8-9+9-3-4-5-9+2)^{33} &:= (8-5-8-9-9-3+45-9-2)^{11} \\ &:= (8+5+8+9-9+3-4-5-9+2)^{11} &:= (-8+5-8-9-9-3+45-9-2)^{33} \\ &:= (8+5+8-9+9+3-4-5-9+2)^{11} &:= (-8-5+8-9-9-3+45-9-2)^{11} \\ &:= (8-5-8+9+9-3+4-5-9+2)^{33} &:= (-8+5-8-9-9+3+45-9-2)^{11} \\ &:= (-8-5+8+9+9-3+4-5-9+2)^{33} &:= (-8-5-8-9-9+3+45-9+2)^{33} \\ &:= (8-5-8+9+9+3+4-5-9+2)^{11} &:= (8+5+8+9+9-3-45+9+2)^{33} \\ &:= (-8+5-8+9+9+3+4-5-9+2)^{33} &:= (8+5+8+9+9+3-45+9+2)^{11} \\ &:= (-8-5+8+9+9+3+4-5-9+2)^{11} &:= (-85+89+9-3+4+5-9-2)^{11} \\ &:= (8-5+8+9-9-3-4+5-9+2)^{33} &:= (-85+89+9-3-4-5+9-2)^{11} \end{aligned}$$

$:= (85 - 89 + 9 - 3 + 4 - 5 + 9 - 2)^{11}$ $:= (-85 + 89 - 9 - 3 + 4 + 5 + 9 - 2)^{11}$ $:= (-85 + 89 + 9 - 3 + 4 - 5 - 9 + 2)^{33}$ $:= (-85 + 89 + 9 + 3 + 4 - 5 - 9 + 2)^{11}$ $:= (85 - 89 + 9 + 3 - 4 + 5 - 9 + 2)^{33}$ $:= (-85 + 89 - 9 - 3 + 4 - 5 + 9 + 2)^{33}$ $:= (-85 + 89 - 9 + 3 + 4 - 5 + 9 + 2)^{11}$ $:= (85 - 89 - 9 + 3 - 4 + 5 + 9 + 2)^{33}$ $:= (-8 - 58 - 9 + 93 - 4 + 5 - 9 - 2)^{11}$ $:= (-8 - 58 - 9 + 93 - 4 - 5 - 9 + 2)^{33}$ $:= (8 + 58 + 9 - 93 + 4 + 5 + 9 + 2)^{33}$ $:= (8 + 58 - 9 - 9 - 34 + 5 - 9 - 2)^{11}$ $:= (8 + 58 - 9 - 9 - 34 - 5 - 9 + 2)^{33}$ $:= (8 - 58 + 9 + 9 + 34 - 5 + 9 + 2)^{11}$ $:= (-8 - 58 + 9 + 9 + 34 + 5 + 9 + 2)^{33}$ $:= (-8 + 58 + 9 + 9 - 3 + 4 - 59 - 2)^{11}$ $:= (-8 - 58 + 9 + 9 - 3 - 4 + 59 - 2)^{33}$ $:= (-8 - 58 + 9 + 9 + 3 - 4 + 59 - 2)^{11}$ $:= (8 - 58 + 9 - 9 - 3 + 4 + 59 - 2)^{11}$ $:= (8 - 58 - 9 + 9 - 3 + 4 + 59 - 2)^{11}$ $:= (8 + 58 + 9 - 9 - 3 - 4 - 59 + 2)^{33}$ $:= (8 + 58 - 9 + 9 - 3 - 4 - 59 + 2)^{33}$ $:= (8 + 58 + 9 - 9 + 3 - 4 - 59 + 2)^{11}$ $:= (8 + 58 - 9 + 9 + 3 - 4 - 59 + 2)^{11}$ $:= (-8 - 58 + 9 - 9 + 3 + 4 + 59 + 2)^{33}$ $:= (-8 - 58 - 9 + 9 + 3 + 4 + 59 + 2)^{33}$ $:= (-8 - 58 - 9 - 9 + 3 - 4 - 5 + 92)^{33}$ $:= (-8 - 5 + 89 - 9 - 3 - 45 - 9 - 2)^{11}$ $:= (8 + 5 - 8 + 99 - 3 + 4 - 5 - 92)^{11}$ $:= (-8 + 5 + 8 + 99 - 3 + 4 - 5 - 92)^{11}$ $:= (8 - 5 - 8 + 99 - 3 + 4 + 5 - 92)^{11}$ $:= (-8 + 5 - 8 + 99 - 3 + 4 + 5 - 92)^{33}$ $:= (-8 - 5 + 8 + 99 - 3 + 4 + 5 - 92)^{11}$ $:= (-8 + 5 - 8 + 99 + 3 + 4 + 5 - 92)^{11}$ $:= (8 + 5 + 8 - 99 - 3 - 4 - 5 + 92)^{33}$ $:= (8 + 5 + 8 - 99 + 3 - 4 - 5 + 92)^{11}$ $:= (8 - 5 + 8 - 99 - 3 - 4 + 5 + 92)^{33}$ $:= (8 + 5 - 8 - 99 + 3 - 4 + 5 + 92)^{33}$	$:= (8 - 5 + 8 - 99 + 3 - 4 + 5 + 92)^{11}$ $:= (-8 + 5 + 8 - 99 + 3 - 4 + 5 + 92)^{33}$ $:= (-8 + 5 - 8 - 9 + 93 - 4 - 59 - 2)^{11}$ $:= (-8 - 5 - 8 - 9 + 93 - 4 - 59 + 2)^{33}$ $:= (8 + 5 + 8 + 9 - 93 + 4 + 59 + 2)^{33}$ $:= (8 - 5 + 8 - 9 + 93 + 4 - 5 - 92)^{33}$ $:= (-8 + 5 - 8 + 9 + 93 + 4 + 5 - 92)^{11}$ $:= (8 + 5 + 8 - 9 - 93 - 4 - 5 + 92)^{33}$ $:= (8 - 5 - 8 + 9 - 93 + 4 - 5 + 92)^{33}$ $:= (-8 - 5 + 8 + 9 - 93 + 4 - 5 + 92)^{33}$ $:= (8 - 5 + 8 - 9 - 93 - 4 + 5 + 92)^{33}$ $:= (8 - 5 + 8 + 9 + 9 + 34 - 59 - 2)^{33}$ $:= (-8 - 5 - 8 + 9 - 9 - 34 + 59 - 2)^{33}$ $:= (-8 - 5 - 8 - 9 + 9 - 34 + 59 - 2)^{33}$ $:= (85 + 8 + 9 - 9 - 34 - 59 + 2)^{33}$ $:= (85 + 8 - 9 + 9 - 34 - 59 + 2)^{33}$ $:= (-85 - 8 + 9 - 9 + 34 + 59 + 2)^{33}$ $:= (-85 - 8 - 9 + 9 + 34 + 59 + 2)^{33}$ $:= (8 - 58 + 99 - 3 - 45 + 9 - 2)^{11}$ $:= (8 + 58 - 99 - 3 + 45 - 9 + 2)^{33}$ $:= (8 + 58 - 99 + 3 + 45 - 9 + 2)^{11}$ $:= (-8 - 58 + 99 + 3 - 45 + 9 + 2)^{33}$ $:= (8 + 58 - 9 - 93 + 45 - 9 + 2)^{33}$ $:= (-8 - 58 + 9 + 93 - 45 + 9 + 2)^{33}$ $:= (-8 - 58 + 9 + 9 + 3 - 45 + 92)^{33}$ $:= (-8 + 5 - 89 + 9 + 34 + 59 - 2)^{11}$ $:= (8 + 5 + 89 - 9 - 34 - 59 + 2)^{33}$ $:= (-8 - 5 - 89 + 9 + 34 + 59 + 2)^{33}$ $:= (-85 - 89 + 93 - 4 - 5 + 92)^{33}$ $:= (-85 + 89 - 93 + 4 - 5 + 92)^{33}$ $:= (858 - 9 - 934 - 5 + 92)^{33}$ $:= (858 - 993 + 45 + 92)^{33}$ $8598667441 := (85986 + 6744 - 1)^2$ $8602933504 := (8 - 602 + 93350 - 4)^2$ $8653650625 := (8 - 65 + 365 - 06 - 2 + 5)^4$ $:= (-8 - 65 + 365 + 06 + 2 + 5)^4$ $:= (8 - 6 + 5 + 365 - 062 - 5)^4$ $:= (8 - 6 - 5 + 365 - 062 + 5)^4$
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$$\begin{aligned}
 & := (-86 - 5 + 365 + 06 + 25)^4 \\
 \mathbf{8657930304} & := (8 - 6 + 5 + 7 + 93030 + 4)^2 \\
 \mathbf{8688663369} & := (86886 + 6336 - 9)^2 \\
 \mathbf{8723933604} & := (8 + 7 + 23 + 93360 + 4)^2 \\
 \mathbf{8756093476} & := (87 + 5 + 6 + 093476)^2 \\
 \mathbf{8784937984} & := (8 - 78 + 4 + 93798 - 4)^2 \\
 & := (8 - 78 - 4 + 93798 + 4)^2 \\
 \mathbf{8793938176} & := (-87 + 93938 + 1 - 76)^2 \\
 \mathbf{8818423496} & := (881 + 842 + 349 - 6)^3 \\
 \mathbf{8822657041} & := (88226 + 5704 - 1)^2 \\
 \mathbf{8862527881} & := (8 + 86252 + 7881)^2 \\
 \mathbf{8945187241} & := (-8 + 94518 + 72 - 4 + 1)^2 \\
 \mathbf{8945565561} & := (8 + 94556 + 5 + 5 + 6 + 1)^2 \\
 \mathbf{8945754724} & := (8 + 94575 + 4 - 7 - 2 + 4)^2 \\
 \mathbf{8947078921} & := (-8 + 94707 - 89 - 21)^2 \\
 \mathbf{8994815281} & := (8 + 9 + 94815 + 2 + 8 - 1)^2 \\
 & := (8 - 9 + 94815 + 28 - 1)^2 \\
 \mathbf{8995004964} & := (-89 + 95004 - 9 - 64)^2 \\
 \mathbf{8998912000} & := (89 + 9 - 8 - 9 - 1 + 2000)^3 \\
 & := (89 - 9 - 8 + 9 - 1 + 2000)^3 \\
 & := (89 - 9 + 8 - 9 + 1 + 2000)^3 \\
 & := (-8 + 9 - 9 + 89 - 1 + 2000)^3 \\
 & := (-8 - 9 + 9 + 89 - 1 + 2000)^3 \\
 & := (8 - 9 - 9 + 89 + 1 + 2000)^3 \\
 \mathbf{8999178496} & := (89 + 99 - 1 + 78 + 49 - 6)^4 \\
 & := (-89 - 99 + 1 + 7 - 8 + 496)^4 \\
 & := (-89 - 99 - 1 - 7 + 8 + 496)^4 \\
 & := (-89 - 9 - 91 - 7 + 8 + 496)^4 \\
 & := (89 - 99 - 178 + 496)^4 \\
 \mathbf{9025950025} & := (-9 + 02 + 5 + 95002 + 5)^2 \\
 \mathbf{9039207968} & := (90 - 3 + 9 + 2 - 07 + 9 + 6 - 8)^5 \\
 & := (90 - 3 + 9 + 2 + 07 - 9 - 6 + 8)^5 \\
 & := (90 - 3 + 9 - 2 - 07 + 9 - 6 + 8)^5 \\
 & := (90 - 3 - 9 + 2 + 07 + 9 - 6 + 8)^5 \\
 & := (90 + 3 + 9 - 2 - 07 - 9 + 6 + 8)^5 \\
 & := (90 + 3 - 9 + 2 + 07 - 9 + 6 + 8)^5 \\
 & := (90 + 3 - 9 - 2 - 07 + 9 + 6 + 8)^5 \\
 & := (9 - 03 + 92 - 07 + 9 + 6 - 8)^5 \\
 & := (9 - 03 + 92 + 07 - 9 - 6 + 8)^5 \\
 & := (-9 - 03 + 92 + 07 + 9 - 6 + 8)^5 \\
 & := (-9 + 03 + 92 + 07 - 9 + 6 + 8)^5 \\
 & := (9 - 03 + 9 + 2 + 079 - 6 + 8)^5 \\
 & := (9 + 03 - 9 + 2 + 079 + 6 + 8)^5 \\
 & := (-9 + 03 + 9 + 2 + 079 + 6 + 8)^5 \\
 & := (9 - 03 + 9 + 2 - 07 + 96 - 8)^5 \\
 & := (9 + 03 - 9 - 2 - 07 + 96 + 8)^5 \\
 & := (-9 + 03 + 9 - 2 - 07 + 96 + 8)^5 \\
 & := (-9 + 03 - 9 + 2 + 07 + 96 + 8)^5 \\
 & := (90 - 3 + 9 + 20 - 7 - 9 + 6 - 8)^5 \\
 & := (90 - 3 - 9 + 20 - 7 + 9 + 6 - 8)^5 \\
 & := (90 - 3 - 9 + 20 + 7 - 9 - 6 + 8)^5 \\
 & := (90 + 3 + 9 - 20 - 7 + 9 + 6 + 8)^5 \\
 & := (9 + 039 + 20 + 7 + 9 + 6 + 8)^5 \\
 & := (9 + 039 - 2 - 07 - 9 + 68)^5 \\
 & := (-9 + 039 + 2 + 07 - 9 + 68)^5 \\
 & := (-9 + 039 - 2 - 07 + 9 + 68)^5 \\
 & := (9 - 03 - 9 + 20 + 79 - 6 + 8)^5 \\
 & := (-9 - 03 + 9 + 20 + 79 - 6 + 8)^5 \\
 & := (-9 + 03 - 9 + 20 + 79 + 6 + 8)^5 \\
 & := (9 - 03 - 9 + 20 - 7 + 96 - 8)^5 \\
 & := (-9 - 03 + 9 + 20 - 7 + 96 - 8)^5 \\
 & := (9 + 03 + 9 - 20 - 7 + 96 + 8)^5 \\
 & := (90 - 3 + 92 - 079 + 6 - 8)^5 \\
 & := (-90 + 3 + 92 + 079 + 6 + 8)^5 \\
 & := (90 - 3 + 92 + 07 - 96 + 8)^5 \\
 & := (90 + 3 - 92 - 07 + 96 + 8)^5 \\
 & := (-90 - 3 - 9 + 207 - 9 - 6 + 8)^5 \\
 & := (9 + 039 - 20 - 7 + 9 + 68)^5 \\
 & := (-9 - 03 - 9 + 207 - 96 + 8)^5 \\
 & := (-90 + 39 + 2 + 079 + 68)^5 \\
 & := (-903 + 920 + 79 - 6 + 8)^5 \\
 & := (-903 + 920 - 7 + 96 - 8)^5 \\
 & := (90 + 39 - 20 - 79 + 68)^5 \\
 \mathbf{9048004641} & := (90480 + 04641)^2 \\
 \mathbf{9109557136} & := (-91 + 095571 - 36)^2 \\
 \mathbf{9116621361} & := (9 + 1 + 1 - 66 + 2 + 1 + 361)^4
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 &:= (91 + 16 - 6 + 213 - 6 + 1)^4 & &:= (9 + 47 - 4 + 2 + 9 - 6 - 8 - 9 + 6)^6 \\
 &:= (-9 + 116 - 6 + 213 - 6 + 1)^4 & &:= (-9 + 47 + 4 + 2 - 9 + 6 + 8 - 9 + 6)^6 \\
 &:= (9 + 1 + 166 - 2 + 136 - 1)^4 & &:= (9 + 47 - 4 + 2 - 9 - 6 - 8 + 9 + 6)^6 \\
 &:= (9 - 1 + 166 - 2 + 136 + 1)^4 & &:= (-9 + 47 - 4 + 2 + 9 - 6 - 8 + 9 + 6)^6 \\
 &:= (9 + 1 - 1 + 662 - 1 - 361)^4 & &:= (9 - 4 + 7 + 42 + 9 + 6 - 8 - 9 - 6)^6 \\
 &:= (9 - 1 + 1 + 662 - 1 - 361)^4 & &:= (9 + 4 - 7 + 42 + 9 - 6 - 8 + 9 - 6)^6 \\
 &:= (9 - 1 - 1 + 662 + 1 - 361)^4 & &:= (9 - 4 + 7 + 42 - 9 + 6 - 8 + 9 - 6)^6 \\
 &:= (-9 + 1 + 1 - 66 + 21 + 361)^4 & &:= (-9 - 4 + 7 + 42 + 9 + 6 - 8 + 9 - 6)^6 \\
 &:= (9 - 1 + 1662 - 1361)^4 & &:= (9 - 4 + 7 + 42 + 9 - 6 - 8 - 9 + 6)^6 \\
 \mathbf{9139551201} &:= (91 - 3 + 95512 + 01)^2 & &:= (-9 + 4 + 7 + 42 - 9 + 6 + 8 - 9 + 6)^6 \\
 \mathbf{9174957796} &:= (9 + 1 + 7 - 4 + 95779 - 6)^2 & &:= (9 - 4 + 7 + 42 - 9 - 6 - 8 + 9 + 6)^6 \\
 \mathbf{9174957796} &:= (-9 - 1 + 7 + 4 + 95779 + 6)^2 & &:= (-9 - 4 + 7 + 42 + 9 - 6 - 8 + 9 + 6)^6 \\
 \mathbf{9208180736} &:= (9 + 2081 + 8 + 07 - 3 - 6)^3 & &:= (9 + 4 + 7 - 4 + 29 + 6 - 8 + 9 - 6)^6 \\
 &:= (-9 + 2081 + 8 + 07 + 3 + 6)^3 & &:= (9 - 4 + 7 + 4 + 29 + 6 - 8 + 9 - 6)^6 \\
 \mathbf{9216960025} &:= (-9 + 2 - 1 + 6 + 96002 + 5)^2 & &:= (-9 + 4 + 7 + 4 + 29 + 6 + 8 - 9 + 6)^6 \\
 \mathbf{9228868489} &:= (9228 + 86848 - 9)^2 & &:= (9 + 4 + 7 - 4 + 29 - 6 - 8 + 9 + 6)^6 \\
 \mathbf{9235210000} &:= (92 + 3 + 5 + 210 + 000)^4 & &:= (9 - 4 + 7 + 4 + 29 - 6 - 8 + 9 + 6)^6 \\
 \mathbf{9274236301} &:= (-9 + 2742 - 3 - 630 + 1)^3 & &:= (-9 + 4 - 7 + 4 - 2 - 9 + 68 - 9 + 6)^6 \\
 \mathbf{9296430724} &:= (-9 + 2 + 96430 - 7 - 2 + 4)^2 & &:= (-9 - 4 - 7 - 4 + 2 - 9 - 6 + 89 - 6)^6 \\
 &:= (-9 - 2 + 96430 - 7 + 2 + 4)^2 & &:= (-9 + 47 - 4 + 29 + 6 - 8 - 9 - 6)^6 \\
 \mathbf{9316496484} &:= (9 + 31 - 6 + 4 + 96484)^2 & &:= (-9 + 47 - 4 + 29 - 6 - 8 - 9 + 6)^6 \\
 \mathbf{9354951841} &:= (9 + 354 - 9 + 5 + 1 - 8 - 41)^4 & &:= (9 - 47 - 4 + 2 + 9 - 6 + 89 - 6)^6 \\
 &:= (-9 + 354 + 9 + 5 + 1 - 8 - 41)^4 & &:= (9 + 4 + 7 - 42 - 9 - 6 + 89 - 6)^6 \\
 &:= (-93 - 5 + 495 - 1 - 84 - 1)^4 & &:= (-9 + 4 + 7 - 42 + 9 - 6 + 89 - 6)^6 \\
 &:= (9 - 3 - 5 + 495 - 184 - 1)^4 & &:= (9 + 4 - 7 + 4 - 29 + 68 - 9 + 6)^6 \\
 &:= (-9 + 3 + 5 + 495 - 184 + 1)^4 & &:= (-9 + 4 - 7 + 4 - 29 + 68 + 9 + 6)^6 \\
 \mathbf{9383796900} &:= (-9 - 3 - 8 - 3 - 7 + 96900)^2 & &:= (-9 + 4 + 7 - 4 - 29 - 6 + 89 - 6)^6 \\
 \mathbf{9435596769} &:= (9 + 4 + 355 + 96769)^2 & &:= (-9 - 4 + 7 + 4 - 29 - 6 + 89 - 6)^6 \\
 \mathbf{9474296896} &:= (9 + 4 + 7 + 4 + 2 + 9 + 6 + 8 - 9 + 6)^6 & &:= (-94 + 74 - 2 - 9 - 6 + 89 - 6)^6 \\
 &:= (9 + 4 + 7 + 4 + 2 - 9 + 6 + 8 + 9 + 6)^6 & &:= (-94 + 7 + 42 + 96 - 8 + 9 - 6)^6 \\
 &:= (9 + 4 - 7 + 4 - 2 + 9 + 6 + 8 + 9 + 6)^6 & &:= (-94 + 7 + 42 + 9 - 6 - 8 + 96)^6 \\
 &:= (-9 + 4 + 7 + 4 + 2 + 9 + 6 + 8 + 9 + 6)^6 & &:= (-9 - 47 - 4 + 29 - 6 + 89 - 6)^6 \\
 &:= (9 + 47 - 4 + 2 + 9 + 6 - 8 - 9 - 6)^6 & &:= (9 + 47 - 4 + 2 + 96 - 8 - 96)^6 \\
 &:= (9 + 47 - 4 - 2 + 9 - 6 + 8 - 9 - 6)^6 & &:= (9 + 47 - 4 + 2 - 96 - 8 + 96)^6 \\
 &:= (9 + 47 - 4 + 2 - 9 + 6 - 8 + 9 - 6)^6 & &:= (-9 - 4 + 74 - 2 - 96 + 89 - 6)^6 \\
 &:= (-9 + 47 - 4 + 2 + 9 + 6 - 8 + 9 - 6)^6 & &:= (9 - 4 + 7 + 42 + 96 - 8 - 96)^6 \\
 &:= (9 + 47 - 4 - 2 - 9 - 6 + 8 + 9 - 6)^6 & &:= (9 - 4 + 7 + 42 - 96 - 8 + 96)^6 \\
 &:= (-9 + 47 - 4 - 2 + 9 - 6 + 8 + 9 - 6)^6 & &:= (947 - 4 + 2 - 9 + 6 - 896)^6
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 & := (94 - 7 - 42 + 96 - 89 - 6)^6 & := (9 + 5 - 09 - 9 + 004 + 99)^5 \\
 & := (94 + 7 - 42 - 96 + 89 - 6)^6 & := (-9 + 5 + 09 - 9 + 004 + 99)^5 \\
 \mathbf{9475854336} & := (9 - 4 - 7 - 5 - 8 - 5 - 4 + 336)^4 & := (-9 + 5 - 09 + 9 + 004 + 99)^5 \\
 & := (-9 + 4 - 7 + 5 - 8 - 5 - 4 + 336)^4 & := (9 + 50 + 9 - 9 + 0049 - 9)^5 \\
 & := (-9 + 4 - 7 - 5 - 8 + 5 - 4 + 336)^4 & := (9 + 50 - 9 + 9 + 0049 - 9)^5 \\
 & := (-9 - 4 - 7 + 5 - 8 - 5 + 4 + 336)^4 & := (-9 + 50 + 9 + 9 + 0049 - 9)^5 \\
 & := (-9 - 4 - 7 - 5 - 8 + 5 + 4 + 336)^4 & := (9 + 50 - 9 - 9 + 0049 + 9)^5 \\
 & := (9 - 47 + 5 + 8 + 5 - 4 + 336)^4 & := (-9 + 50 + 9 - 9 + 0049 + 9)^5 \\
 & := (9 - 4 - 75 - 8 + 54 + 336)^4 & := (-9 + 50 - 9 + 9 + 0049 + 9)^5 \\
 & := (-9 - 4 - 7 - 58 + 54 + 336)^4 & := (95 + 099 + 004 - 99)^5 \\
 & := (94 + 758 - 543 - 3 + 6)^4 & := (-95 + 099 - 004 + 99)^5 \\
 \mathbf{9508980196} & := (9 - 508 + 98019 - 6)^2 & := (95 - 099 + 004 + 99)^5 \\
 \mathbf{9509900499} & := (95 + 09 + 9 + 004 - 9 - 9)^5 & := (95 + 09 + 90 + 04 - 99)^5 \\
 & := (95 + 09 - 9 + 004 + 9 - 9)^5 & := (-95 + 09 + 90 - 04 + 99)^5 \\
 & := (95 - 09 + 9 + 004 + 9 - 9)^5 & := (95 - 09 - 90 + 04 + 99)^5 \\
 & := (95 + 09 - 9 + 004 - 9 + 9)^5 & := (950 + 9 - 900 + 49 - 9)^5 \\
 & := (95 - 09 + 9 + 004 - 9 + 9)^5 & := (950 - 9 - 900 + 49 + 9)^5 \\
 & := (95 - 09 - 9 + 004 + 9 + 9)^5 & := (-9 + 509 - 900 + 499)^5 \\
 & := (9 + 50 + 9 + 9 + 004 + 9 + 9)^5 & \mathbf{9597924961} := (9 + 5 - 9 + 7 - 9 + 249 + 61)^4 \\
 & := (9 + 5 + 099 + 004 - 9 - 9)^5 & := (-9 + 5 + 9 + 7 - 9 + 249 + 61)^4 \\
 & := (9 - 5 + 099 - 004 + 9 - 9)^5 & := (-9 + 5 - 9 + 7 + 9 + 249 + 61)^4 \\
 & := (-9 + 5 + 099 + 004 + 9 - 9)^5 & := (95 + 97 + 9 + 2 + 49 + 61)^4 \\
 & := (9 - 5 + 099 - 004 - 9 + 9)^5 & := (95 + 9 + 7 + 92 + 49 + 61)^4 \\
 & := (-9 + 5 + 099 + 004 - 9 + 9)^5 & := (9 + 5 + 97 + 92 + 49 + 61)^4 \\
 & := (-9 - 5 + 099 - 004 + 9 + 9)^5 & \mathbf{9622822383} := (-96 - 2 - 2 - 8 + 2238 - 3)^3 \\
 & := (9 + 5 + 09 + 90 + 04 - 9 - 9)^5 & \mathbf{9649918756} := (-964 + 99187 + 5 + 6)^2 \\
 & := (9 - 5 + 09 + 90 - 04 + 9 - 9)^5 & \mathbf{9655617169} := (96556 + 1716 - 9)^2 \\
 & := (9 + 5 - 09 + 90 + 04 + 9 - 9)^5 & \mathbf{9677214091} := (9 + 6 - 7 - 7 + 2140 - 9 - 1)^3 \\
 & := (-9 + 5 + 09 + 90 + 04 + 9 - 9)^5 & := (-9 + 6 - 7 - 7 + 2140 + 9 - 1)^3 \\
 & := (9 - 5 + 09 + 90 - 04 - 9 + 9)^5 & := (-9 - 6 + 7 + 7 + 2140 - 9 + 1)^3 \\
 & := (9 + 5 - 09 + 90 + 04 - 9 + 9)^5 & := (-96 + 77 + 2140 + 9 + 1)^3 \\
 & := (-9 + 5 + 09 + 90 + 04 - 9 + 9)^5 & := (96 - 7 - 7 + 2140 - 91)^3 \\
 & := (9 - 5 - 09 + 90 - 04 + 9 + 9)^5 & \mathbf{9689842969} := (9 + 6 + 8 + 98429 - 6 - 9)^2 \\
 & := (-9 - 5 + 09 + 90 - 04 + 9 + 9)^5 & := (9 - 6 + 8 + 98429 + 6 - 9)^2 \\
 & := (-9 + 5 - 09 + 90 + 04 + 9 + 9)^5 & := (-9 + 6 + 8 + 98429 - 6 + 9)^2 \\
 & := (9 - 5 + 09 - 9 - 004 + 99)^5 & := (-9 - 6 + 8 + 98429 + 6 + 9)^2 \\
 & := (9 - 5 - 09 + 9 - 004 + 99)^5 & := (9 + 68 + 98429 - 69)^2 \\
 & := (-9 - 5 + 09 + 9 - 004 + 99)^5 & \mathbf{9718142104} := (9 + 7 + 1 + 8 + 1 + 4 + 2104)^3
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 & := (-9 + 718 + 1421 + 04)^3 \\
 & := (-9 + 7 + 18 + 14 + 2104)^3 \\
 \mathbf{9721171216} & := (97 + 211 - 7 - 1 - 2 + 16)^4 \\
 & := (97 - 2 + 11 - 7 - 1 + 216)^4 \\
 & := (9 + 72 + 11 + 7 - 1 + 216)^4 \\
 & := (9 + 72 + 1 + 17 - 1 + 216)^4 \\
 & := (9 + 72 - 1 + 17 + 1 + 216)^4 \\
 & := (-9 - 7 - 2 + 117 - 1 + 216)^4 \\
 \mathbf{9783979396} & := (978 + 3 + 97939 - 6)^2 \\
 \mathbf{9801990025} & := (-9 + 8 - 01 + 99002 + 5)^2 \\
 & := (98118 + 930 + 2 + 5)^2 \\
 \mathbf{9817639056} & := (98176 - 3 + 905 + 6)^2 \\
 \mathbf{9822990321} & := (98229 + 903 - 21)^2 \\
 \mathbf{9825963876} & := (98259 - 6 - 3 + 876)^2 \\
 \mathbf{9845799076} & := (98 + 45 + 7 + 99076)^2 \\
 & := (9 + 84 + 57 + 99076)^2 \\
 \mathbf{9849371536} & := (98493 + 715 + 36)^2 \\
 \mathbf{9869031649} & := (98690 + 3 + 1 + 649)^2 \\
 \mathbf{9879763609} & := (98797 - 6 - 3 + 609)^2 \\
 \mathbf{9901245025} & := (99012 - 4 + 502 - 5)^2 \\
 \mathbf{9911994481} & := (99119 - 9 + 448 + 1)^2 \\
 & := (99 + 11 + 99448 + 1)^2 \\
 \mathbf{9913985761} & := (991 + 3 + 98576 - 1)^2 \\
 \mathbf{9925738384} & := (99257 + 383 - 8 - 4)^2 \\
 \mathbf{9926136900} & := (99261 + 369 + 00)^2 \\
 \mathbf{9926336161} & := (99263 + 361 + 6 + 1)^2 \\
 \mathbf{9931318336} & := (99313 - 1 + 8 + 336)^2 \\
 \mathbf{9940688209} & := (99406 + 88 + 209)^2 \\
 \mathbf{9942682369} & := (99426 - 82 + 369)^2 \\
 \mathbf{9952248951} & := (-99 + 5 + 2248 - 9 + 5 + 1)^3 \\
 \mathbf{9953055225} & := (99530 + 5 + 5 + 225)^2 \\
 \mathbf{9957046225} & := (99570 - 4 - 6 + 225)^2 \\
 \mathbf{9960439204} & := (99604 + 3 - 9 + 204)^2 \\
 \mathbf{9971220736} & := (99 + 7 + 12 + 207 - 3 - 6)^4 \\
 & := (9 + 97 + 12 + 207 - 3 - 6)^4 \\
 & := (-9 + 97 + 12 + 207 + 3 + 6)^4 \\
 & := (-9 - 9 + 71 + 220 + 7 + 36)^4 \\
 & := (9 - 9 + 71 + 2 + 207 + 36)^4 \\
 & := (-9 + 9 + 71 + 2 + 207 + 36)^4 \\
 \mathbf{9973217956} & := (99732 - 1 + 79 + 56)^2 \\
 \mathbf{9973817161} & := (99738 - 1 + 71 + 61)^2 \\
 \mathbf{9975415129} & := (99754 - 1 - 5 + 129)^2 \\
 \mathbf{9977212996} & := (99772 + 129 - 9 - 6)^2 \\
 \mathbf{9978211881} & := (99782 + 118 - 8 - 1)^2 \\
 \mathbf{9979810201} & := (99798 + 102 - 01)^2 \\
 \mathbf{9980010000} & := (99800 + 100 + 00)^2 \\
 \mathbf{9980209801} & := (99802 + 098 + 01)^2 \\
 \mathbf{9981808281} & := (99818 + 082 + 8 + 1)^2 \\
 & := (99818 + 08 + 2 + 81)^2 \\
 \mathbf{9982807396} & := (99828 - 07 - 3 + 96)^2 \\
 \mathbf{9983606724} & := (99836 + 06 + 72 + 4)^2 \\
 \mathbf{9984406084} & := (99844 - 06 + 084)^2 \\
 \mathbf{9984805776} & := (99848 + 05 + 77 - 6)^2 \\
 \mathbf{9987403969} & := (99874 + 03 - 9 + 69)^2 \\
 \mathbf{9988403364} & := (99884 - 03 - 3 + 64)^2 \\
 \mathbf{9989003025} & := (99890 + 030 + 25)^2 \\
 \mathbf{9991002025} & := (99910 + 020 + 25)^2 \\
 \mathbf{9991201936} & := (99912 - 01 + 9 + 36)^2 \\
 \mathbf{9992801296} & := (99928 + 01 + 29 + 6)^2 \\
 \mathbf{9997200196} & := (99972 - 001 + 9 + 6)^2 \\
 \mathbf{9997800121} & := (99978 + 0012 - 1)^2 \\
 \mathbf{9998000100} & := (99980 + 0010 + 0)^2 \\
 \mathbf{9998200081} & := (99982 + 0008 + 1)^2 \\
 \mathbf{9999800001} & := (99998 + 00001)^2
 \end{aligned}$$

7.10 11-Digits Semi-Selfie Numbers

$$\begin{aligned}
 \mathbf{10000000000} & := (10 + 000000000)^{10} & & := (100000 + 00000)^2 \\
 & := (100 + 00000000)^5 & & \mathbf{10000200001} := (100002 + 0000 - 1)^2
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 10001800081 &:= (100018 + 000 - 8 - 1)^2 \\
 10002000100 &:= (100020 - 0010 + 0)^2 \\
 10002200121 &:= (100022 - 0012 + 1)^2 \\
 10002800196 &:= (100028 + 001 - 9 - 6)^2 \\
 10007201296 &:= (100072 - 01 - 29 - 6)^2 \\
 10008801936 &:= (100088 + 01 - 9 - 36)^2 \\
 10009002025 &:= (100090 - 020 - 25)^2 \\
 10011003025 &:= (100110 - 030 - 25)^2 \\
 10011603364 &:= (100116 + 03 + 3 - 64)^2 \\
 10012603969 &:= (100126 - 03 + 9 - 69)^2 \\
 10015205776 &:= (100152 - 05 - 77 + 6)^2 \\
 10015606084 &:= (100156 + 06 - 084)^2 \\
 10016406724 &:= (100164 - 06 - 72 - 4)^2 \\
 10017207396 &:= (100172 + 07 + 3 - 96)^2 \\
 10018208281 &:= (100182 - 082 - 8 - 1)^2 \\
 &:= (100182 - 08 - 2 - 81)^2 \\
 10019809801 &:= (100198 - 098 - 01)^2 \\
 10020010000 &:= (100200 - 100 + 00)^2 \\
 10020210201 &:= (100202 - 102 + 01)^2 \\
 10021011025 &:= (-1002 + 101102 + 5)^2 \\
 10021811881 &:= (100218 - 118 + 8 + 1)^2 \\
 10022812996 &:= (100228 - 129 + 9 + 6)^2 \\
 10024615129 &:= (100246 + 1 + 5 - 129)^2 \\
 10026217161 &:= (100262 + 1 - 71 - 61)^2 \\
 10026817956 &:= (100268 + 1 - 79 - 56)^2 \\
 10039639204 &:= (100396 - 3 + 9 - 204)^2 \\
 10043046225 &:= (100430 + 4 + 6 - 225)^2 \\
 10047055225 &:= (100470 - 5 - 5 - 225)^2 \\
 10057482369 &:= (100574 + 82 - 369)^2 \\
 10059488209 &:= (100594 - 88 - 209)^2 \\
 10068918336 &:= (100689 - 1 - 8 - 336)^2 \\
 10074538384 &:= (100745 + 3 + 8 - 384)^2 \\
 10104873529 &:= (101048 + 7 - 3 - 529)^2 \\
 10120963609 &:= (101209 + 6 - 3 - 609)^2 \\
 10137469225 &:= (101374 - 692 - 2 + 5)^2 \\
 10137670596 &:= (101376 - 705 + 9 + 6)^2 \\
 10147842125 &:= (-10 - 1 + 47 + 8 - 4 + 2125)^3 \\
 10161244809 &:= (101612 + 4 - 4 - 809)^2 \\
 10161244809 &:= (101612 - 4 + 4 - 809)^2 \\
 10161648025 &:= (101616 - 4 - 802 - 5)^2
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 10165680625 &:= (101656 - 806 - 25)^2 \\
 10190094916 &:= (101900 - 949 + 1 - 6)^2 \\
 10192719681 &:= (101927 + 1 - 968 - 1)^2 \\
 10192719681 &:= (101927 - 1 - 968 + 1)^2 \\
 10225861129 &:= (102258 - 6 - 1129)^2 \\
 10226063376 &:= (-1 + 02 - 2 - 6 - 06 + 337 - 6)^4 \\
 &:= (-1 - 02 + 2 - 6 - 06 + 337 - 6)^4 \\
 &:= (-1 - 02 + 260 + 63 - 3 + 7 - 6)^4 \\
 &:= (1 - 02 + 260 + 63 - 3 - 7 + 6)^4 \\
 &:= (-1 + 02 - 2 - 60 + 6 - 3 + 376)^4 \\
 &:= (-1 - 02 + 2 - 60 + 6 - 3 + 376)^4 \\
 &:= (1 + 02 + 2 - 60 - 6 + 3 + 376)^4 \\
 &:= (-1 + 02 - 2 + 6 - 063 + 376)^4 \\
 &:= (-1 - 02 + 2 + 6 - 063 + 376)^4 \\
 &:= (10 + 226 + 06 + 3 - 3 + 76)^4 \\
 &:= (10 + 226 + 06 - 3 + 3 + 76)^4 \\
 &:= (10 + 2 + 260 + 6 - 3 + 37 + 6)^4 \\
 &:= (-10 - 2 + 260 - 6 + 3 - 3 + 76)^4 \\
 &:= (-10 - 2 + 260 - 6 - 3 + 3 + 76)^4 \\
 10355301121 &:= (1 + 03 + 5 + 5 + 301 + 1 + 2 + 1)^4 \\
 &:= (-1 + 0355 - 30 - 1 - 1 - 2 - 1)^4 \\
 &:= (1 - 03 + 5 - 5 + 301 - 1 + 21)^4 \\
 &:= (1 - 03 - 5 + 5 + 301 - 1 + 21)^4 \\
 &:= (-1 - 03 + 5 - 5 + 301 + 1 + 21)^4 \\
 &:= (-1 - 03 - 5 + 5 + 301 + 1 + 21)^4 \\
 &:= (-10 + 355 - 3 - 01 - 1 - 21)^4 \\
 &:= (-10 + 35 - 5 + 301 + 1 - 2 - 1)^4 \\
 &:= (-10 + 35 - 5 + 301 - 1 - 2 + 1)^4 \\
 &:= (10 - 3 + 5 - 5 + 301 + 12 - 1)^4 \\
 &:= (10 - 3 - 5 + 5 + 301 + 12 - 1)^4 \\
 &:= (-1 + 0355 - 3 - 011 - 21)^4 \\
 &:= (1 + 035 - 5 + 301 - 12 - 1)^4 \\
 &:= (-1 + 035 - 5 + 301 - 12 + 1)^4 \\
 &:= (10 + 35 - 5 + 301 - 1 - 21)^4 \\
 &:= (-103 + 5 + 530 - 112 - 1)^4 \\
 &:= (-103 + 5 - 5 + 301 + 121)^4 \\
 &:= (-103 - 5 + 5 + 301 + 121)^4 \\
 10391151969 &:= (103911 - 5 - 1969)^2 \\
 10460353203 &:= (-1 + 04 + 6 - 03 + 5 - 3 - 2 - 03)^{21} \\
 &:= (1 - 04 + 6 + 03 + 5 - 3 - 2 - 03)^{21}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} &:= (1 - 04 + 6 - 03 + 5 + 3 - 2 - 03)^{21} \\ &:= (-1 + 04 - 6 + 03 + 5 + 3 - 2 - 03)^{21} \\ &:= (-1 + 04 + 6 + 03 - 5 - 3 + 2 - 03)^{21} \\ &:= (1 + 04 - 6 + 03 + 5 - 3 + 2 - 03)^{21} \\ &:= (-1 + 04 + 6 - 03 - 5 + 3 + 2 - 03)^{21} \\ &:= (1 - 04 + 6 + 03 - 5 + 3 + 2 - 03)^{21} \\ &:= (1 + 04 - 6 - 03 + 5 + 3 + 2 - 03)^{21} \\ &:= (1 - 04 + 6 - 03 + 5 - 3 - 2 + 03)^{21} \\ &:= (-1 + 04 - 6 + 03 + 5 - 3 - 2 + 03)^{21} \\ &:= (-1 - 04 + 6 + 03 - 5 + 3 - 2 + 03)^{21} \\ &:= (-1 + 04 - 6 - 03 + 5 + 3 - 2 + 03)^{21} \\ &:= (1 - 04 - 6 + 03 + 5 + 3 - 2 + 03)^{21} \\ &:= (-1 + 04 + 6 - 03 - 5 - 3 + 2 + 03)^{21} \\ &:= (1 - 04 + 6 + 03 - 5 - 3 + 2 + 03)^{21} \\ &:= (1 + 04 - 6 - 03 + 5 - 3 + 2 + 03)^{21} \\ &:= (1 - 04 + 6 - 03 - 5 + 3 + 2 + 03)^{21} \\ &:= (-1 + 04 - 6 + 03 - 5 + 3 + 2 + 03)^{21} \\ &:= (1 + 04 + 6 + 03 + 5 + 3 + 2 + 03)^7 \\ &:= (-1 + 04 - 6 - 03 - 5 - 3 + 20 - 3)^{21} \\ &:= (1 - 04 - 6 + 03 - 5 - 3 + 20 - 3)^{21} \\ &:= (1 + 04 + 6 - 03 + 5 - 3 + 20 - 3)^7 \\ &:= (1 - 04 - 6 - 03 - 5 + 3 + 20 - 3)^{21} \\ &:= (-1 + 04 + 6 + 03 - 5 + 3 + 20 - 3)^7 \\ &:= (1 + 04 - 6 + 03 + 5 + 3 + 20 - 3)^7 \\ &:= (-1 + 04 + 6 + 03 + 5 + 3 - 20 + 3)^{21} \\ &:= (1 - 04 - 6 - 03 - 5 - 3 + 20 + 3)^{21} \\ &:= (-1 + 04 + 6 + 03 - 5 - 3 + 20 + 3)^7 \\ &:= (1 + 04 - 6 + 03 + 5 - 3 + 20 + 3)^7 \\ &:= (-1 + 04 + 6 - 03 - 5 + 3 + 20 + 3)^7 \\ &:= (1 - 04 + 6 + 03 - 5 + 3 + 20 + 3)^7 \\ &:= (1 + 04 - 6 - 03 + 5 + 3 + 20 + 3)^7 \\ &:= (10 - 4 - 6 + 035 - 3 - 2 - 03)^7 \\ &:= (-10 + 4 + 6 + 035 - 3 - 2 - 03)^7 \\ &:= (-10 + 4 - 6 + 035 + 3 - 2 + 03)^7 \\ &:= (10 - 4 - 6 + 03 - 5 + 32 - 03)^7 \\ &:= (-10 + 4 + 6 + 03 - 5 + 32 - 03)^7 \\ &:= (10 - 4 - 6 - 03 - 5 + 32 + 03)^7 \\ &:= (-10 + 4 + 6 - 03 - 5 + 32 + 03)^7 \\ &:= (-1 + 046 + 03 + 5 - 3 - 20 - 3)^7 \\ &:= (-1 + 046 - 03 + 5 + 3 - 20 - 3)^7 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} &:= (-1 + 046 - 03 + 5 - 3 - 20 + 3)^7 \\ &:= (-1 - 04 + 60 + 3 - 5 - 3 - 20 - 3)^7 \\ &:= (-1 - 04 + 60 - 3 - 5 + 3 - 20 - 3)^7 \\ &:= (-1 - 04 + 60 - 3 - 5 - 3 - 20 + 3)^7 \\ &:= (1 - 04 + 6 + 035 - 32 - 03)^{21} \\ &:= (-1 + 04 + 6 - 035 + 32 - 03)^{21} \\ &:= (-1 + 04 - 6 + 035 - 32 + 03)^{21} \\ &:= (1 - 04 + 6 - 035 + 32 + 03)^{21} \\ &:= (-10 + 46 - 035 + 3 + 2 - 03)^{21} \\ &:= (10 - 46 + 035 + 3 - 2 + 03)^{21} \\ &:= (-10 + 46 - 035 - 3 + 2 + 03)^{21} \\ &:= (-10 + 46 - 03 + 5 - 32 - 03)^{21} \\ &:= (-10 - 4 + 60 - 35 - 3 - 2 - 03)^{21} \\ &:= (10 - 4 + 60 - 35 - 3 + 2 - 03)^7 \\ &:= (-10 + 4 + 60 - 35 + 3 + 2 + 03)^7 \\ &:= (-10 + 4 + 60 + 3 - 53 + 2 - 03)^{21} \\ &:= (10 + 4 - 60 - 3 + 53 + 2 - 03)^{21} \\ &:= (10 - 4 - 60 + 3 + 53 - 2 + 03)^{21} \\ &:= (-10 + 4 + 60 - 3 - 53 + 2 + 03)^{21} \\ &:= (-10 - 4 + 60 - 3 - 5 - 32 - 03)^{21} \\ &:= (-10 + 4 + 60 + 3 + 5 - 32 - 03)^7 \\ &:= (-10 + 4 + 60 - 3 + 5 - 32 + 03)^7 \\ &:= (-10 + 4 - 6 + 035 + 3 - 20 - 3)^{21} \\ &:= (10 - 4 + 6 + 035 + 3 - 20 - 3)^7 \\ &:= (-10 + 4 - 6 + 035 - 3 - 20 + 3)^{21} \\ &:= (10 - 4 + 6 + 035 - 3 - 20 + 3)^7 \\ &:= (10 - 4 + 6 - 035 + 3 + 20 + 3)^{21} \\ &:= (10 - 4 - 6 - 03 + 53 - 20 - 3)^7 \\ &:= (-10 + 4 + 6 - 03 + 53 - 20 - 3)^7 \\ &:= (-10 + 4 - 6 + 03 + 53 - 20 + 3)^7 \\ &:= (-10 + 46 - 035 + 3 + 20 + 3)^7 \\ &:= (-10 + 46 + 03 - 53 + 20 - 3)^{21} \\ &:= (10 - 46 + 03 + 53 - 20 + 3)^{21} \\ &:= (-10 + 46 - 03 - 53 + 20 + 3)^{21} \\ &:= (10 + 4 - 60 + 35 - 3 + 20 - 3)^{21} \\ &:= (10 - 4 + 60 - 3 - 53 + 20 - 3)^7 \\ &:= (10 + 4 - 60 + 3 + 53 + 20 - 3)^7 \\ &:= (-10 + 4 + 60 + 3 - 53 + 20 + 3)^7 \\ &:= (10 + 4 - 60 - 3 + 53 + 20 + 3)^7 \end{aligned}$$

10510100501 := (105 + 1 + 01 - 005 - 01) ⁵	:= (1 - 060 - 4 - 4 - 9 + 93 - 7 + 3) ⁹
:= (105 + 1 - 01 - 005 + 01) ⁵	:= (1 + 060 - 4 - 4 + 9 - 9 - 37 - 3) ⁹
:= (105 - 1 + 01 - 005 + 01) ⁵	:= (1 + 060 - 4 - 4 - 9 + 9 - 37 - 3) ⁹
:= (1 + 05 + 101 - 005 - 01) ⁵	:= (-1 + 06 - 044 + 9 + 9 + 37 - 3) ⁹
:= (1 - 05 + 101 + 005 - 01) ⁵	:= (-1 + 06 - 044 - 9 - 9 - 3 + 73) ⁹
:= (-1 + 05 + 101 - 005 + 01) ⁵	:= (-1 - 06 - 04 + 49 + 9 - 37 + 3) ⁹
:= (-1 - 05 + 101 + 005 + 01) ⁵	:= (-1 + 06 - 04 - 49 - 9 - 3 + 73) ⁹
:= (1 + 05 + 1 + 0100 - 5 - 01) ⁵	:= (10 + 60 - 44 + 9 - 9 - 3 - 7 - 3) ⁹
:= (1 - 05 + 1 + 0100 + 5 - 01) ⁵	:= (10 + 60 - 44 - 9 + 9 - 3 - 7 - 3) ⁹
:= (1 + 05 - 1 + 0100 - 5 + 01) ⁵	:= (10 - 60 + 44 + 9 + 9 - 3 + 7 - 3) ⁹
:= (-1 + 05 + 1 + 0100 - 5 + 01) ⁵	:= (-10 + 60 - 44 + 9 - 9 + 3 + 7 - 3) ⁹
:= (1 - 05 - 1 + 0100 + 5 + 01) ⁵	:= (-10 + 60 - 44 - 9 + 9 + 3 + 7 - 3) ⁹
:= (-1 - 05 + 1 + 0100 + 5 + 01) ⁵	:= (-10 + 60 - 44 + 9 - 9 - 3 + 7 + 3) ⁹
:= (105 + 10 - 10 - 05 + 01) ⁵	:= (-10 + 60 - 44 - 9 + 9 - 3 + 7 + 3) ⁹
:= (105 - 10 + 10 - 05 + 01) ⁵	:= (10 + 60 - 4 - 49 + 9 - 3 - 7 - 3) ⁹
:= (10 + 5 - 10 + 100 - 5 + 01) ⁵	:= (10 - 60 + 4 + 49 + 9 - 3 + 7 - 3) ⁹
:= (-10 + 5 + 10 + 100 - 5 + 01) ⁵	:= (-10 + 60 - 4 - 49 + 9 + 3 + 7 - 3) ⁹
:= (10 - 5 - 10 + 100 + 5 + 01) ⁵	:= (-10 + 60 + 4 - 49 + 9 + 3 - 7 + 3) ⁹
:= (-10 - 5 + 10 + 100 + 5 + 01) ⁵	:= (-10 + 60 - 4 - 49 + 9 - 3 + 7 + 3) ⁹
:= (1 + 051 + 0100 - 50 - 1) ⁵	:= (-10 - 6 + 04 - 4 + 99 + 3 - 73) ⁹
:= (-1 + 051 + 0100 - 50 + 1) ⁵	:= (-10 - 6 - 04 + 4 + 99 + 3 - 73) ⁹
:= (1 - 051 + 0100 + 50 + 1) ⁵	:= (-10 - 6 + 04 - 4 + 9 + 93 - 73) ⁹
:= (10 - 510 + 100 + 501) ⁵	:= (-10 - 6 - 04 + 4 + 9 + 93 - 73) ⁹
10517853871 := (105 - 1785 + 3871) ³	:= (10 + 6 + 04 + 4 + 9 - 93 + 73) ⁹
10567428804 := (105674 - 2880 + 4) ²	:= (1 + 060 + 44 - 99 + 3 + 7 - 3) ⁹
10604499373 := (10 + 6 - 04 - 4 + 9 + 9 - 3 - 7 - 3) ⁹	:= (1 + 060 + 44 - 99 - 3 + 7 + 3) ⁹
:= (10 - 6 + 04 + 4 + 9 - 9 - 3 + 7 - 3) ⁹	:= (1 + 060 + 44 - 9 - 93 + 7 + 3) ⁹
:= (10 - 6 + 04 + 4 - 9 + 9 - 3 + 7 - 3) ⁹	:= (10 + 60 + 4 + 4 - 99 + 37 - 3) ⁹
:= (10 + 6 + 04 + 4 - 9 - 9 + 3 + 7 - 3) ⁹	:= (-10 + 60 - 4 - 4 - 99 - 3 + 73) ⁹
:= (-10 + 6 - 04 - 4 + 9 + 9 + 3 + 7 - 3) ⁹	:= (-10 + 60 - 4 - 4 - 9 - 93 + 73) ⁹
:= (10 - 6 - 04 - 4 + 9 + 9 + 3 - 7 + 3) ⁹	:= (1060 - 44 - 993 - 7 - 3) ⁹
:= (-10 + 6 + 04 - 4 + 9 + 9 + 3 - 7 + 3) ⁹	10617447681 := (1061 - 744 + 7 + 6 - 8 - 1) ⁴
:= (-10 + 6 - 04 + 4 + 9 + 9 + 3 - 7 + 3) ⁹	:= (-106 - 17 + 447 + 6 - 8 - 1) ⁴
:= (10 + 6 + 04 + 4 - 9 - 9 - 3 + 7 + 3) ⁹	:= (-10 - 61 - 7 + 4 + 476 - 81) ⁴
:= (-10 + 6 - 04 - 4 + 9 + 9 - 3 + 7 + 3) ⁹	10671096601 := (-10 + 6710 + 96601) ²
:= (-1 + 06 - 04 - 4 - 9 - 9 + 37 - 3) ⁹	10720765125 := (107 + 2076 + 5 + 12 + 5) ³
:= (-10 - 6 - 04 + 49 - 9 + 3 - 7 - 3) ⁹	10750371856 := (1 - 07 - 50 + 371 + 8 + 5 - 6) ⁴
:= (-10 - 6 - 04 + 49 - 9 - 3 - 7 + 3) ⁹	:= (1 + 07 - 50 + 371 - 8 - 5 + 6) ⁴
:= (-1 - 060 + 4 - 4 - 9 + 93 - 7 - 3) ⁹	:= (-1 - 07 - 50 + 371 + 8 - 5 + 6) ⁴
:= (-1 - 060 - 4 + 4 - 9 + 93 - 7 - 3) ⁹	:= (1 - 07 + 5 + 0371 + 8 - 56) ⁴

$$\begin{aligned} & := (-1 - 07 + 50 + 371 - 85 - 6)^4 \\ & := (-107 + 503 - 71 + 8 - 5 - 6)^4 \\ & := (107 + 50 + 3 + 71 + 85 + 6)^4 \\ & := (10 + 7 + 503 - 7 - 185 - 6)^4 \\ & := (10 - 7 + 503 + 7 - 185 - 6)^4 \\ & := (10 + 7503 - 7185 - 6)^4 \\ \mathbf{10779215329} & := (10 + 7 + 7 + 9 - 2 + 1 + 5 + 3 - 2 + 9)^6 \\ & := (10 + 7 + 7 + 9 + 2 - 1 + 5 - 3 + 2 + 9)^6 \\ & := (1 + 077 - 9 - 2 - 1 - 5 - 3 - 2 - 9)^6 \\ & := (-1 + 077 - 9 - 2 + 1 - 5 - 3 - 2 - 9)^6 \\ & := (1 + 07 + 7 + 9 - 2 + 15 + 3 - 2 + 9)^6 \\ & := (-1 + 07 + 7 + 9 + 2 + 15 - 3 + 2 + 9)^6 \\ & := (-1 + 07 - 7 + 9 - 2 - 1 + 53 - 2 - 9)^6 \\ & := (-1 - 07 + 7 + 9 - 2 - 1 + 53 - 2 - 9)^6 \\ & := (-1 + 07 + 7 - 9 + 2 - 1 + 53 - 2 - 9)^6 \\ & := (-1 + 07 + 7 - 9 - 2 - 1 + 53 + 2 - 9)^6 \\ & := (-1 + 07 - 7 - 9 - 2 - 1 + 53 - 2 + 9)^6 \\ & := (-1 - 07 + 7 - 9 - 2 - 1 + 53 - 2 + 9)^6 \\ & := (-1 + 07 + 7 + 9 - 2 - 1 + 5 + 32 - 9)^6 \\ & := (1 + 07 - 7 + 9 + 2 - 1 - 5 + 32 + 9)^6 \\ & := (1 - 07 + 7 + 9 + 2 - 1 - 5 + 32 + 9)^6 \\ & := (-1 + 07 - 7 + 9 + 2 + 1 - 5 + 32 + 9)^6 \\ & := (-1 - 07 + 7 + 9 + 2 + 1 - 5 + 32 + 9)^6 \\ & := (-1 + 07 + 7 - 9 - 2 - 1 + 5 + 32 + 9)^6 \\ & := (-10 + 7 + 7 + 9 + 21 + 5 - 3 + 2 + 9)^6 \\ & := (10 + 7 - 7 + 9 - 2 - 1 + 5 - 3 + 29)^6 \\ & := (10 - 7 + 7 + 9 - 2 - 1 + 5 - 3 + 29)^6 \\ & := (10 + 7 + 7 - 9 + 2 - 1 + 5 - 3 + 29)^6 \\ & := (-10 + 7 + 7 + 9 + 2 + 1 + 5 - 3 + 29)^6 \\ & := (10 + 7 - 7 + 9 + 2 - 1 - 5 + 3 + 29)^6 \\ & := (10 - 7 + 7 + 9 + 2 - 1 - 5 + 3 + 29)^6 \\ & := (-10 + 7 + 7 + 9 - 2 - 1 + 5 + 3 + 29)^6 \\ & := (1 + 077 + 9 - 21 - 5 - 3 - 2 - 9)^6 \\ & := (-1 + 077 - 9 - 21 + 5 + 3 + 2 - 9)^6 \\ & := (1 + 077 - 9 - 21 - 5 - 3 - 2 + 9)^6 \\ & := (1 + 077 + 9 - 2 - 1 - 5 - 3 - 29)^6 \\ & := (-1 + 077 + 9 - 2 + 1 - 5 - 3 - 29)^6 \\ & := (-1 + 077 - 9 + 2 - 1 + 5 + 3 - 29)^6 \\ & := (1 + 077 - 9 - 2 + 1 + 5 + 3 - 29)^6 \\ & := (1 + 07 + 7 + 9 - 21 - 5 - 3 - 2 - 9)^6 \\ & := (-1 - 07 + 7 + 9 - 21 + 5 + 3 - 2 - 9)^6 \\ & := (1 - 07 + 7 + 9 - 21 + 5 - 3 + 2 - 9)^6 \\ & := (1 + 07 + 7 + 9 - 2 - 1 - 5 - 3 - 29)^6 \\ & := (-1 + 07 + 7 + 9 - 2 + 1 - 5 - 3 - 29)^6 \\ & := (1 - 07 + 7 + 9 + 2 - 1 + 5 - 3 - 29)^6 \\ & := (-1 - 07 + 7 + 9 + 2 + 1 + 5 - 3 - 29)^6 \\ & := (-1 - 07 + 7 + 9 + 2 + 1 + 5 - 3 - 29)^6 \\ & := (-1 - 07 + 7 + 9 + 2 + 1 + 5 - 3 - 29)^6 \\ & := (-1 - 07 + 7 + 9 - 21 + 53 + 2 - 9)^6 \\ & := (-1 + 07 - 7 + 9 - 21 + 53 - 2 + 9)^6 \\ & := (-1 - 07 + 7 + 9 - 21 + 53 - 2 + 9)^6 \\ & := (-1 + 07 + 7 - 9 - 21 + 53 + 2 + 9)^6 \\ & := (-1 + 07 - 7 + 9 + 21 - 5 + 32 - 9)^6 \\ & := (-1 - 07 + 7 + 9 + 21 - 5 + 32 - 9)^6 \\ & := (-1 + 07 - 7 - 9 + 21 - 5 + 32 + 9)^6 \\ & := (-1 - 07 + 7 - 9 + 21 - 5 + 32 + 9)^6 \\ & := (-1 + 07 + 7 + 9 - 21 + 5 + 32 + 9)^6 \\ & := (-1 + 07 - 7 + 9 - 2 + 15 - 3 + 29)^6 \\ & := (-1 - 07 + 7 + 9 - 2 + 15 - 3 + 29)^6 \\ & := (-1 + 07 + 7 - 9 + 2 + 15 - 3 + 29)^6 \\ & := (-1 + 07 + 7 + 9 + 2 - 1 + 53 - 29)^6 \\ & := (1 + 07 + 7 + 9 - 2 + 1 + 53 - 29)^6 \\ & := (10 + 77 - 9 - 2 - 15 - 3 - 2 - 9)^6 \\ & := (10 + 77 + 9 - 2 - 1 - 53 - 2 + 9)^6 \\ & := (10 + 77 + 9 - 2 - 1 - 5 - 32 - 9)^6 \\ & := (10 + 77 - 9 - 2 - 1 - 5 - 32 + 9)^6 \\ & := (-10 + 77 + 9 - 2 + 1 - 5 - 32 + 9)^6 \\ & := (10 + 7 + 79 - 2 - 1 - 53 - 2 + 9)^6 \\ & := (10 + 7 + 79 - 2 - 1 - 5 - 32 - 9)^6 \\ & := (10 - 7 + 79 + 2 - 1 + 5 - 32 - 9)^6 \\ & := (-10 + 7 + 79 - 2 + 1 - 5 - 32 + 9)^6 \\ & := (-10 - 7 + 79 + 2 + 1 + 5 - 32 + 9)^6 \\ & := (10 - 7 - 7 + 92 + 1 - 53 + 2 + 9)^6 \\ & := (-10 + 7 - 7 + 92 + 1 + 5 - 32 - 9)^6 \\ & := (-10 - 7 + 7 + 92 + 1 + 5 - 32 - 9)^6 \\ & := (10 - 7 - 7 + 9 + 21 - 5 - 3 + 29)^6 \\ & := (-10 + 7 + 7 - 9 + 21 + 5 - 3 + 29)^6 \\ & := (-10 + 7 - 7 + 9 + 21 - 5 + 3 + 29)^6 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 & := (-10 - 7 + 7 + 9 + 21 - 5 + 3 + 29)^6 \\
 & := (10 + 7 - 7 + 9 + 2 - 15 + 32 + 9)^6 \\
 & := (10 - 7 + 7 + 9 + 2 - 15 + 32 + 9)^6 \\
 & := (1 + 077 - 92 + 1 + 53 - 2 + 9)^6 \\
 & := (-1 + 077 - 92 - 1 + 53 + 2 + 9)^6 \\
 & := (1 + 077 + 9 - 2 - 15 - 32 + 9)^6 \\
 & := (-1 - 07 + 79 + 2 + 15 - 32 - 9)^6 \\
 & := (1 + 07 + 79 - 2 - 15 - 32 + 9)^6 \\
 & := (107 - 79 + 2 - 1 - 5 + 32 - 9)^6 \\
 & := (107 + 7 - 92 + 15 + 3 - 2 + 9)^6 \\
 & := (107 + 7 - 9 - 21 - 5 - 3 - 29)^6 \\
 & := (107 + 7 - 9 - 2 - 15 - 32 - 9)^6 \\
 & := (10 - 77 + 92 + 1 - 5 - 3 + 29)^6 \\
 & := (10 + 77 + 9 - 21 - 5 - 32 + 9)^6 \\
 & := (10 + 77 + 9 - 2 - 15 - 3 - 29)^6 \\
 & := (-10 - 7 + 79 + 21 + 5 - 32 - 9)^6 \\
 & := (10 + 7 + 79 - 21 - 5 - 32 + 9)^6 \\
 & := (10 + 7 + 79 - 2 - 15 - 3 - 29)^6 \\
 & := (-10 - 7 + 79 + 2 + 15 - 3 - 29)^6 \\
 & := (10 - 7 - 7 + 92 - 15 + 3 - 29)^6 \\
 & := (-1 + 077 - 9 + 2153 - 2 - 9)^3 \\
 & := (1 + 07 + 7 - 92 + 153 - 29)^6 \\
 & := (107 - 79 + 2 - 15 + 3 + 29)^6 \\
 & := (107 + 7 - 92 + 1 + 53 - 29)^6 \\
 & := (-1 + 077 + 9 + 2153 - 29)^3 \\
 & := (1 - 077 + 9 - 215 + 329)^6 \\
 & := (-1 + 07 + 79 + 2153 - 29)^3 \\
 \mathbf{10823192128} & := (108 - 2 - 31 + 9 + 2128)^3 \\
 & := (108 - 2 - 3 - 19 + 2128)^3 \\
 \mathbf{10884540241} & := (-1 + 088 + 4 - 5 - 4 + 0241)^4 \\
 & := (-1 + 088 - 4 - 5 + 4 + 0241)^4 \\
 & := (-1 + 08 - 84 - 5 + 402 + 4 - 1)^4 \\
 & := (-1 + 08 + 84 - 5 - 4 + 0241)^4 \\
 & := (-1 + 088 - 45 + 40 + 241)^4 \\
 & := (-108 - 84 + 540 - 24 - 1)^4 \\
 & := (108 - 84 + 540 - 241)^4 \\
 \mathbf{10896752313} & := (-1 - 089 + 6 - 7 - 5 + 2313)^3 \\
 & := (1 - 089 - 6 - 7 + 5 + 2313)^3 \\
 & := (-10 + 8 - 96 + 7 - 5 + 2313)^3 \\
 & := (10 - 8 - 96 - 7 + 5 + 2313)^3 \\
 & := (-10 - 8 - 9 + 6 - 75 + 2313)^3 \\
 \mathbf{10999394884} & := (1 + 09993 + 94884)^2 \\
 \mathbf{11012193721} & := (-1 + 101219 + 3721)^2 \\
 \mathbf{11019960576} & := (11 + 01 + 9 + 9 + 6 - 05 - 7 - 6)^8 \\
 & := (11 - 01 + 9 + 9 - 6 - 05 + 7 - 6)^8 \\
 & := (-11 - 01 + 9 + 9 + 6 + 05 + 7 - 6)^8 \\
 & := (11 + 01 + 9 + 9 - 6 - 05 - 7 + 6)^8 \\
 & := (-11 + 01 + 9 + 9 + 6 + 05 - 7 + 6)^8 \\
 & := (-11 - 01 + 9 + 9 - 6 + 05 + 7 + 6)^8 \\
 & := (11 + 01 - 9 - 9 + 6 + 05 + 7 + 6)^8 \\
 & := (1 + 10 + 1 + 9 + 9 + 6 - 05 - 7 - 6)^8 \\
 & := (1 + 10 - 1 + 9 + 9 - 6 - 05 + 7 - 6)^8 \\
 & := (-1 + 10 + 1 + 9 + 9 - 6 - 05 + 7 - 6)^8 \\
 & := (-1 - 10 - 1 + 9 + 9 + 6 + 05 + 7 - 6)^8 \\
 & := (1 + 10 + 1 + 9 + 9 - 6 - 05 - 7 + 6)^8 \\
 & := (-1 + 10 - 1 + 9 - 9 + 6 + 05 - 7 + 6)^8 \\
 & := (-1 + 10 - 1 - 9 + 9 + 6 + 05 - 7 + 6)^8 \\
 & := (1 - 10 - 1 + 9 + 9 + 6 + 05 - 7 + 6)^8 \\
 & := (-1 - 10 + 1 + 9 + 9 + 6 + 05 - 7 + 6)^8 \\
 & := (-1 - 10 - 1 + 9 + 9 - 6 + 05 + 7 + 6)^8 \\
 & := (1 + 10 + 1 - 9 - 9 + 6 + 05 + 7 + 6)^8 \\
 & := (1 + 1 + 019 + 9 + 6 - 05 - 7 - 6)^8 \\
 & := (1 - 1 + 019 + 9 - 6 - 05 + 7 - 6)^8 \\
 & := (-1 + 1 + 019 + 9 - 6 - 05 + 7 - 6)^8 \\
 & := (1 + 1 + 019 + 9 - 6 - 05 - 7 + 6)^8 \\
 & := (-1 - 1 + 019 - 9 + 6 + 05 - 7 + 6)^8 \\
 & := (-1 - 1 - 01 + 99 - 60 - 5 - 7 - 6)^8 \\
 & := (1 + 1 + 01 + 9 + 9 + 60 - 57 - 6)^8 \\
 & := (-1 - 1 - 01 + 9 + 9 - 60 + 57 + 6)^8 \\
 & := (-1 - 1 - 01 + 9 - 9 - 60 + 5 + 76)^8 \\
 & := (-1 - 1 - 01 - 9 + 9 - 60 + 5 + 76)^8 \\
 & := (110 - 1 + 9 - 96 - 05 + 7 - 6)^8 \\
 & := (110 + 1 + 9 - 96 - 05 - 7 + 6)^8 \\
 & := (110 + 1 - 9 - 9 + 6 - 05 - 76)^8 \\
 & := (-11 - 019 - 9 + 6 + 057 - 6)^8 \\
 & := (-11 - 019 - 9 - 6 + 057 + 6)^8 \\
 & := (-11 - 01 + 99 - 6 - 057 - 6)^8 \\
 & := (11 + 01 - 9 + 96 - 05 - 76)^8 \\
 & := (-1 + 101 - 9 - 9 - 60 - 5 + 7 - 6)^8 \\
 & := (1 + 101 - 9 - 9 - 60 - 5 - 7 + 6)^8
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 &:= (-1 - 10 - 19 - 9 + 6 + 057 - 6)^8 \\
 &:= (-1 - 10 - 19 - 9 - 6 + 057 + 6)^8 \\
 &:= (-1 - 10 - 1 + 99 - 6 - 057 - 6)^8 \\
 &:= (1 + 10 + 1 - 9 + 96 - 05 - 76)^8 \\
 &:= (110 - 19 - 9 - 60 - 5 + 7 - 6)^8 \\
 &:= (-110 - 1 + 9 + 9 + 60 + 57 - 6)^8 \\
 &:= (110 + 1 + 9 + 9 - 60 - 57 + 6)^8 \\
 &:= (11 + 019 - 9 + 60 - 57 - 6)^8 \\
 &:= (11 + 019 + 9 + 60 - 5 - 76)^8 \\
 &:= (1 + 10 + 19 - 9 + 60 - 57 - 6)^8 \\
 &:= (1 + 10 + 19 + 9 + 60 - 5 - 76)^8 \\
 &:= (1 + 1 + 0199 + 60 + 57 + 6)^4 \\
 &:= (-110 - 19 + 96 + 057 - 6)^8 \\
 &:= (1 + 101 + 99 + 60 + 57 + 6)^4 \\
 &:= (-1 - 101 + 99 - 60 + 5 + 76)^8 \\
 \mathbf{11033611681} &:= (-1 + 103361 + 1681)^2 \\
 \mathbf{11040808032} &:= (11 + 04 + 080 + 8 - 03 + 2)^5 \\
 &:= (11 + 04 + 08 + 080 - 3 + 2)^5 \\
 &:= (-1 + 104 + 08 - 08 - 03 + 2)^5 \\
 &:= (-1 + 104 - 08 + 08 - 03 + 2)^5 \\
 &:= (-1 + 10 + 4 + 080 + 8 + 03 - 2)^5 \\
 &:= (1 + 10 + 4 + 080 + 8 - 03 + 2)^5 \\
 &:= (-1 + 10 + 4 + 08 + 080 + 3 - 2)^5 \\
 &:= (1 + 10 + 4 + 08 + 080 - 3 + 2)^5 \\
 &:= (1 + 1 - 04 + 080 - 8 + 032)^5 \\
 &:= (1 + 1 - 04 - 08 + 080 + 32)^5 \\
 &:= (-11 + 040 + 80 - 8 + 03 - 2)^5 \\
 &:= (-11 + 040 - 8 + 080 + 3 - 2)^5 \\
 &:= (-1 - 10 + 40 + 80 - 8 + 03 - 2)^5 \\
 &:= (1 - 10 + 40 + 80 - 8 - 03 + 2)^5 \\
 &:= (-1 - 10 + 40 - 8 + 080 + 3 - 2)^5 \\
 &:= (1 - 10 + 40 - 8 + 080 - 3 + 2)^5 \\
 &:= (110 + 40 - 8 - 08 - 032)^5 \\
 &:= (110 - 40 + 8 - 08 + 032)^5 \\
 &:= (110 - 40 - 8 + 08 + 032)^5 \\
 &:= (-1 + 104 + 080 - 80 - 3 + 2)^5 \\
 &:= (-1 + 104 - 080 + 80 - 3 + 2)^5 \\
 &:= (110 - 40 + 80 - 80 + 32)^5 \\
 &:= (110 - 40 - 80 + 80 + 32)^5 \\
 \mathbf{11044538649} &:= (-1 + 104453 - 8 + 649)^2 \\
 \mathbf{11048532544} &:= (1 + 104853 + 254 + 4)^2 \\
 \mathbf{11050634884} &:= (-1 + 105063 + 48 + 8 + 4)^2 \\
 \mathbf{11050845129} &:= (-1 + 105084 + 51 - 2 - 9)^2 \\
 \mathbf{11051265625} &:= (1 + 105126 - 5 + 6 + 2 - 5)^2 \\
 \mathbf{11060939241} &:= (1 + 106093 - 924 + 1)^2 \\
 \mathbf{11105365924} &:= (1 + 1 + 105365 + 9 + 2 + 4)^2 \\
 &:= (1 + 1 + 105365 - 9 + 24)^2 \\
 \mathbf{11134383337} &:= (-1113 + 4 - 3 + 8 + 3337)^3 \\
 \mathbf{11154105769} &:= (-1 - 1 - 154 + 105769)^2 \\
 \mathbf{11156640625} &:= (-1 - 1 - 1 - 5 - 66 + 406 - 2 - 5)^4 \\
 &:= (-11 - 1 - 56 - 6 + 406 - 2 - 5)^4 \\
 &:= (-1 - 11 - 56 - 6 + 406 - 2 - 5)^4 \\
 &:= (-111 + 5 + 6 - 6 + 406 + 25)^4 \\
 &:= (-111 + 5 - 6 + 6 + 406 + 25)^4 \\
 \mathbf{11224377919} &:= (11 + 2243 - 7 - 7 + 9 - 1 - 9)^3 \\
 &:= (11 + 2243 - 7 - 7 - 9 - 1 + 9)^3 \\
 &:= (1 - 1 + 2243 - 7 - 7 - 9 + 19)^3 \\
 &:= (-1 + 1 + 2243 - 7 - 7 - 9 + 19)^3 \\
 \mathbf{11225826304} &:= (112258 - 2 - 6304)^2 \\
 \mathbf{11284642907} &:= (-1128 + 464 + 2907)^3 \\
 \mathbf{11294588176} &:= (11 + 294 + 5 + 8 + 8 - 1 + 7 - 6)^4 \\
 &:= (11 + 294 + 5 + 8 + 8 + 1 - 7 + 6)^4 \\
 &:= (1 - 1 + 294 + 5 + 8 + 8 + 17 - 6)^4 \\
 &:= (-1 + 1 + 294 + 5 + 8 + 8 + 17 - 6)^4 \\
 &:= (-1 - 1 + 294 - 5 + 8 + 8 + 17 + 6)^4 \\
 &:= (1 - 129 + 458 + 8 + 1 - 7 - 6)^4 \\
 &:= (112 + 9 + 45 - 8 - 8 + 176)^4 \\
 &:= (-11 + 294 + 58 + 8 - 17 - 6)^4 \\
 &:= (1 + 1 - 29 - 458 + 817 - 6)^4 \\
 \mathbf{11299742784} &:= (-11 + 2997 + 42 - 784)^3 \\
 \mathbf{11405819251} &:= (1 + 1405 + 819 + 25 + 1)^3 \\
 &:= (1 + 1405 - 81 + 925 + 1)^3 \\
 \mathbf{11417777316} &:= (114177 - 7 - 7316)^2 \\
 \mathbf{11419273321} &:= (114192 - 7332 + 1)^2 \\
 \mathbf{11433811041} &:= (1 - 1 - 4 + 338 - 1 - 1 - 04 - 1)^4 \\
 &:= (-1 + 1 - 4 + 338 - 1 - 1 - 04 - 1)^4 \\
 &:= (-1 - 1 - 4 + 338 + 1 - 1 - 04 - 1)^4 \\
 &:= (-1 - 1 - 4 + 338 - 1 + 1 - 04 - 1)^4 \\
 &:= (-1 - 1 - 4 + 338 - 1 - 1 - 04 + 1)^4 \\
 &:= (-11 - 4 + 338 - 1 + 10 - 4 - 1)^4
 \end{aligned}$$

11716114081 := (-11 - 71 + 6 - 1 - 1 + 408 - 1) ⁴	:= (-1 - 2 + 14 - 9 + 330 + 1 - 7 + 6) ⁴
:= (-1 - 1 - 71 + 6 - 11 + 408 - 1) ⁴	:= (1 - 2 - 1 + 49 - 3 + 301 - 7 - 6) ⁴
:= (11 + 716 + 11 - 408 - 1) ⁴	:= (-1 - 2 + 1 + 49 - 3 + 301 - 7 - 6) ⁴
11821188952 := (11 + 8 + 2118 + 89 + 52) ³	:= (1 + 2 + 1 - 4 - 9 + 330 + 17 - 6) ⁴
:= (1 + 18 + 2118 + 89 + 52) ³	:= (-1 - 2 - 1 + 4 - 9 + 330 + 17 - 6) ⁴
11830695361 := (118306 - 9536 - 1) ²	:= (-1 + 2 - 1 + 4 + 9 + 330 - 17 + 6) ⁴
11914842304 := (-1 - 1 - 9 - 1 + 4 - 8 - 4 + 2304) ³	:= (1 - 2 + 1 + 4 + 9 + 330 - 17 + 6) ⁴
:= (-1 - 1 - 9 - 1 - 4 - 8 + 4 + 2304) ³	:= (12 + 14 + 9 - 3 + 301 - 7 + 6) ⁴
:= (-11 + 9 - 14 - 8 + 4 + 2304) ³	:= (-1 + 214 + 93 + 3 + 017 + 6) ⁴
:= (1 - 19 - 14 + 8 + 4 + 2304) ³	:= (1 + 214 + 9 + 33 - 01 + 76) ⁴
11961853903 := (1196 + 185 + 3 + 903) ³	:= (-1 + 214 + 9 + 33 + 01 + 76) ⁴
11963109376 := (1 - 1 + 9 - 6 - 3 + 109376) ²	:= (1 + 214 + 9 + 3 + 30 - 1 + 76) ⁴
:= (-1 + 1 + 9 - 6 - 3 + 109376) ²	:= (-1 + 214 + 9 + 3 + 30 + 1 + 76) ⁴
:= (1 - 1 - 9 + 6 + 3 + 109376) ²	:= (-1 - 21 + 49 + 3 + 301 + 7 - 6) ⁴
:= (-1 + 1 - 9 + 6 + 3 + 109376) ²	:= (1 - 21 + 49 + 3 + 301 - 7 + 6) ⁴
12003612721 := (1 + 20 + 036 + 1 + 272 + 1) ⁴	:= (-1 + 21 - 4 + 9 + 330 - 17 - 6) ⁴
12024728171 := (1 + 2024 - 7 + 281 - 7 - 1) ³	:= (-1 - 21 + 4 + 9 + 330 + 17 - 6) ⁴
:= (-1 + 2024 - 7 + 281 - 7 + 1) ³	:= (-1 + 2 + 149 + 3 + 3 + 0176) ⁴
12056247757 := (-1 + 2056 + 247 - 7 + 5 - 7) ³	:= (121 + 4 - 93 + 301 - 7 + 6) ⁴
12087822375 := (-1 + 2 - 087 + 8 - 2 + 2375) ³	12166529024 := (12 - 1 + 6 + 6 - 5 + 2 + 90 - 2 - 4) ⁵
:= (-1 - 2 - 087 + 8 + 2 + 2375) ³	:= (12 + 1 + 6 - 6 + 5 + 2 + 90 - 2 - 4) ⁵
:= (-1 + 2 + 08 - 7 - 82 + 2375) ³	:= (12 + 1 - 6 + 6 + 5 + 2 + 90 - 2 - 4) ⁵
:= (1 + 2 - 08 + 7 - 82 + 2375) ³	:= (12 - 1 + 6 + 6 - 5 - 2 + 90 + 2 - 4) ⁵
:= (-12 + 08 - 78 + 2 + 2375) ³	:= (12 + 1 + 6 - 6 + 5 - 2 + 90 + 2 - 4) ⁵
12101100025 := (1 - 2 - 1 + 0110002 + 5) ²	:= (12 + 1 - 6 + 6 + 5 - 2 + 90 + 2 - 4) ⁵
:= (-1 - 2 + 1 + 0110002 + 5) ²	:= (12 - 1 + 6 - 6 - 5 + 2 + 90 + 2 + 4) ⁵
:= (-12 + 10 + 110002 + 5) ²	:= (12 - 1 - 6 + 6 - 5 + 2 + 90 + 2 + 4) ⁵
12149330176 := (1 + 2 - 1 + 4 + 9 + 3 + 301 + 7 + 6) ⁴	:= (12 + 1 - 6 - 6 + 5 + 2 + 90 + 2 + 4) ⁵
:= (-1 + 2 + 1 + 4 + 9 + 3 + 301 + 7 + 6) ⁴	:= (-12 + 1 + 6 + 6 + 5 + 2 + 90 + 2 + 4) ⁵
:= (12 - 1 - 4 + 9 + 330 - 1 - 7 - 6) ⁴	:= (-1 + 21 + 66 + 5 + 2 + 9 - 02 + 4) ⁵
:= (-12 + 1 + 4 + 9 + 330 - 1 + 7 - 6) ⁴	:= (-1 + 21 + 66 + 5 - 2 + 9 + 02 + 4) ⁵
:= (12 + 1 - 4 - 9 + 330 + 1 + 7 - 6) ⁴	:= (-1 + 21 + 6 + 65 + 2 + 9 - 02 + 4) ⁵
:= (-12 - 1 + 4 + 9 + 330 + 1 + 7 - 6) ⁴	:= (-1 + 21 + 6 + 65 - 2 + 9 + 02 + 4) ⁵
:= (-12 + 1 + 4 + 9 + 330 + 1 - 7 + 6) ⁴	:= (-1 + 2 + 16 + 6 - 5 + 2 + 90 - 2 - 4) ⁵
:= (-1 + 21 + 4 + 9 - 3 + 301 + 7 - 6) ⁴	:= (1 + 2 + 16 - 6 + 5 + 2 + 90 - 2 - 4) ⁵
:= (1 + 21 - 4 + 9 + 3 + 301 + 7 - 6) ⁴	:= (-1 + 2 + 16 + 6 - 5 - 2 + 90 + 2 - 4) ⁵
:= (1 + 21 + 4 + 9 - 3 + 301 - 7 + 6) ⁴	:= (1 + 2 + 16 - 6 + 5 - 2 + 90 + 2 - 4) ⁵
:= (-1 + 21 + 4 - 9 + 3 + 301 + 7 + 6) ⁴	:= (-1 - 2 + 16 + 6 - 5 + 2 + 90 + 2 - 4) ⁵
:= (-1 - 2 + 14 - 9 + 330 - 1 + 7 - 6) ⁴	:= (1 - 2 + 16 - 6 + 5 + 2 + 90 + 2 - 4) ⁵
:= (1 - 2 + 14 - 9 + 330 - 1 - 7 + 6) ⁴	:= (-1 - 2 + 16 + 6 - 5 - 2 + 90 - 2 + 4) ⁵

$$\begin{aligned} &:= (1 - 2 + 16 - 6 + 5 - 2 + 90 - 2 + 4)^5 \\ &:= (-1 + 2 + 16 - 6 - 5 + 2 + 90 + 2 + 4)^5 \\ &:= (1 + 2 - 1 + 66 + 5 + 29 - 02 + 4)^5 \\ &:= (-1 + 2 + 1 + 66 + 5 + 29 - 02 + 4)^5 \\ &:= (1 - 2 - 1 + 66 + 5 + 29 + 02 + 4)^5 \\ &:= (-1 - 2 + 1 + 66 + 5 + 29 + 02 + 4)^5 \\ &:= (1 + 2 - 1 + 66 + 5 - 2 + 9 + 024)^5 \\ &:= (-1 + 2 + 1 + 66 + 5 - 2 + 9 + 024)^5 \\ &:= (1 - 2 - 1 + 66 + 5 + 2 + 9 + 024)^5 \\ &:= (-1 - 2 + 1 + 66 + 5 + 2 + 9 + 024)^5 \\ &:= (1 + 2 - 1 + 6 + 65 + 29 - 02 + 4)^5 \\ &:= (-1 + 2 + 1 + 6 + 65 + 29 - 02 + 4)^5 \\ &:= (1 - 2 - 1 + 6 + 65 + 29 + 02 + 4)^5 \\ &:= (-1 - 2 + 1 + 6 + 65 + 29 + 02 + 4)^5 \\ &:= (1 + 2 - 1 + 6 + 65 - 2 + 9 + 024)^5 \\ &:= (-1 + 2 + 1 + 6 + 65 - 2 + 9 + 024)^5 \\ &:= (1 - 2 - 1 + 6 + 65 + 2 + 9 + 024)^5 \\ &:= (-1 - 2 + 1 + 6 + 65 + 2 + 9 + 024)^5 \\ &:= (-12 + 1 + 66 + 52 - 9 + 02 + 4)^5 \\ &:= (-12 - 1 + 6 - 6 + 5 - 2 + 90 + 24)^5 \\ &:= (-12 - 1 - 6 + 6 + 5 - 2 + 90 + 24)^5 \\ &:= (-1 + 21 + 66 - 5 + 29 - 02 - 4)^5 \\ &:= (-1 + 21 + 66 + 5 - 2 - 9 + 024)^5 \\ &:= (1 + 21 - 6 + 65 + 29 - 02 - 4)^5 \\ &:= (-1 + 21 + 6 + 65 - 2 - 9 + 024)^5 \\ &:= (1 - 21 - 6 - 6 + 52 + 90 - 2 - 4)^5 \\ &:= (-1 + 2 + 166 - 52 - 9 + 02 - 4)^5 \\ &:= (-1 - 2 + 166 - 52 - 9 - 02 + 4)^5 \\ &:= (-1 - 2 + 16 + 6 + 52 + 9 + 024)^5 \\ &:= (-1 - 2 - 16 + 6 + 5 - 2 + 90 + 24)^5 \\ &:= (1 + 2 - 16 + 6 - 5 + 2 + 90 + 24)^5 \\ &:= (1 + 2 - 1 + 66 - 52 + 90 + 2 - 4)^5 \\ &:= (-1 + 2 + 1 + 66 - 52 + 90 + 2 - 4)^5 \\ &:= (1 - 2 - 1 + 66 - 52 + 90 - 2 + 4)^5 \\ &:= (-1 - 2 + 1 + 66 - 52 + 90 - 2 + 4)^5 \\ &:= (1 - 2 - 1 - 6 - 6 + 52 + 90 - 24)^5 \\ &:= (-1 - 2 + 1 - 6 - 6 + 52 + 90 - 24)^5 \\ &:= (121 - 66 + 52 - 9 + 02 + 4)^5 \\ &:= (-12 + 16 + 65 + 29 + 02 + 4)^5 \\ &:= (-12 + 16 + 65 + 2 + 9 + 024)^5 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} &:= (-1 + 216 + 6 - 5 + 2 - 90 - 24)^5 \\ &:= (1 + 216 - 6 + 5 + 2 - 90 - 24)^5 \\ &:= (1 + 21 - 66 + 52 + 90 + 2 + 4)^5 \\ &:= (1 - 21 + 66 + 5 + 29 + 024)^5 \\ &:= (1 - 21 + 6 + 65 + 29 + 024)^5 \\ &:= (-1 + 2 + 166 + 5 - 2 - 90 + 24)^5 \\ &:= (-1 - 2 + 166 + 5 + 2 - 90 + 24)^5 \\ &:= (1 + 2 + 1 - 66 + 52 + 90 + 24)^5 \\ &:= (-121 - 66 - 5 + 290 + 2 + 4)^5 \\ &:= (-121 + 6 - 65 + 290 - 2 - 4)^5 \\ &:= (-121 - 6 - 65 + 290 + 2 + 4)^5 \\ &:= (1 - 2 - 166 + 5 + 290 - 24)^5 \\ &:= (1 + 2214 + 6 + 72 + 1 + 2 + 7)^3 \\ &:= (1 + 2214 + 67 + 2 + 12 + 7)^3 \\ &:= (122 + 1 + 46 + 7 + 2127)^3 \\ &:= (1 + 22 + 146 + 7 + 2127)^3 \\ &:= (1 + 22 - 3 + 05 + 9 + 04 + 6 + 4)^6 \\ &:= (-1 - 2 + 23 + 05 + 9 + 04 + 6 + 4)^6 \\ &:= (1 + 2 + 2 - 3 - 05 + 9 + 046 - 4)^6 \\ &:= (-1 + 2 - 2 + 3 - 05 + 9 + 046 - 4)^6 \\ &:= (-1 - 2 + 2 + 3 - 05 + 9 + 046 - 4)^6 \\ &:= (-1 - 2 - 2 - 3 + 05 + 9 + 046 - 4)^6 \\ &:= (1 + 2 + 2 - 3 + 05 - 9 + 046 + 4)^6 \\ &:= (-1 + 2 - 2 + 3 + 05 - 9 + 046 + 4)^6 \\ &:= (-1 - 2 + 2 + 3 + 05 - 9 + 046 + 4)^6 \\ &:= (1 - 2 - 2 - 3 - 05 + 9 + 046 + 4)^6 \\ &:= (1 + 2 + 2 - 3 - 05 - 9 - 04 + 64)^6 \\ &:= (-1 + 2 - 2 + 3 - 05 - 9 - 04 + 64)^6 \\ &:= (-1 - 2 + 2 + 3 - 05 - 9 - 04 + 64)^6 \\ &:= (-1 - 2 - 2 - 3 + 05 - 9 - 04 + 64)^6 \\ &:= (1 - 2 - 2 - 3 - 05 - 9 + 04 + 64)^6 \\ &:= (12 - 2 + 30 + 5 + 9 + 04 - 6 - 4)^6 \\ &:= (12 - 2 + 30 + 5 + 9 - 04 - 6 + 4)^6 \\ &:= (-12 + 2 + 30 + 5 + 9 + 04 + 6 + 4)^6 \\ &:= (-12 - 2 - 3 + 059 + 04 + 6 - 4)^6 \\ &:= (-12 + 2 - 3 + 059 + 04 - 6 + 4)^6 \\ &:= (-12 - 2 - 3 + 059 - 04 + 6 + 4)^6 \\ &:= (1 + 22 - 3 - 05 - 9 + 046 - 4)^6 \\ &:= (-1 - 22 - 3 + 05 + 9 - 04 + 64)^6 \\ &:= (1 - 22 - 3 - 05 + 9 + 04 + 64)^6 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 &:= (-1 - 2 + 23 - 05 - 9 + 046 - 4)^6 \\
 &:= (-1 - 2 - 23 + 05 + 9 - 04 + 64)^6 \\
 &:= (1 - 2 - 23 - 05 + 9 + 04 + 64)^6 \\
 &:= (1 + 2 + 2 - 30 + 59 + 04 + 6 + 4)^6 \\
 &:= (1 - 2 - 2 - 30 + 5 + 90 - 4 - 6 - 4)^6 \\
 &:= (-1 + 2 - 2 - 30 - 5 + 90 + 4 - 6 - 4)^6 \\
 &:= (-1 - 2 + 2 - 30 - 5 + 90 + 4 - 6 - 4)^6 \\
 &:= (-1 - 2 - 2 - 30 - 5 + 90 - 4 + 6 - 4)^6 \\
 &:= (-1 + 2 - 2 - 30 - 5 + 90 - 4 - 6 + 4)^6 \\
 &:= (-1 - 2 + 2 - 30 - 5 + 90 - 4 - 6 + 4)^6 \\
 &:= (122 - 3 + 05 - 90 + 4 + 6 + 4)^6 \\
 &:= (-12 - 23 - 05 + 90 - 4 + 6 - 4)^6 \\
 &:= (-12 + 2 + 30 - 5 - 9 + 046 - 4)^6 \\
 &:= (12 + 2 - 30 + 5 + 9 + 046 + 4)^6 \\
 &:= (12 + 2 - 30 - 5 + 9 - 04 + 64)^6 \\
 &:= (12 + 2 - 30 + 5 - 9 + 04 + 64)^6 \\
 &:= (12 - 2 + 3 - 05 + 90 - 46 - 4)^6 \\
 &:= (12 - 2 + 3 + 05 + 90 + 4 - 64)^6 \\
 &:= (-1 + 22 - 30 + 59 - 04 + 6 - 4)^6 \\
 &:= (-1 - 22 - 30 + 5 + 90 + 4 + 6 - 4)^6 \\
 &:= (-1 - 22 - 30 + 5 + 90 - 4 + 6 + 4)^6 \\
 &:= (1 - 22 - 30 - 5 + 90 + 4 + 6 + 4)^6 \\
 &:= (1 + 2 - 2 + 30 + 59 - 046 + 4)^6 \\
 &:= (1 - 2 + 2 + 30 + 59 - 046 + 4)^6 \\
 &:= (1 + 2 - 2 + 30 - 5 + 90 - 4 - 64)^6 \\
 &:= (1 - 2 + 2 + 30 - 5 + 90 - 4 - 64)^6 \\
 &:= (-12 + 2305 + 9 + 04 - 6 + 4)^3 \\
 &:= (1 + 2230 + 59 + 04 + 6 + 4)^3 \\
 &:= (-1 - 22 - 30 + 59 + 046 - 4)^6 \\
 &:= (1 - 22 - 305 - 90 + 464)^6 \\
 \mathbf{12246522625} &:= (1 + 2246 + 5 - 2 - 2 + 62 - 5)^3 \\
 &:= (1 + 2246 - 5 - 2 - 2 + 62 + 5)^3 \\
 &:= (1 + 22 + 4 + 6 + 5 + 2262 + 5)^3 \\
 &:= (1 + 2 + 24 + 6 + 5 + 2262 + 5)^3 \\
 &:= (1 - 2 - 2 + 46 + 5 + 2262 - 5)^3 \\
 &:= (1 - 2 - 2 + 46 - 5 + 2262 + 5)^3 \\
 &:= (1 + 2246 + 5 + 22 + 6 + 25)^3 \\
 &:= (1 + 2246 + 5 + 2 + 26 + 25)^3 \\
 &:= (1 - 22 + 4 + 65 + 2262 - 5)^3 \\
 &:= (-1 - 22 - 4 + 65 + 2262 + 5)^3
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 &:= (-1 - 2 - 24 + 65 + 2262 + 5)^3 \\
 \mathbf{12262468616} &:= (1 + 2262 + 46 + 8 - 6 + 1 - 6)^3 \\
 &:= (-1 + 2262 + 4 - 6 - 8 + 61 - 6)^3 \\
 &:= (-1 + 2262 - 46 + 86 - 1 + 6)^3 \\
 \mathbf{12294402112} &:= (-1 + 2294 + 4 + 02 + 11 - 2)^3 \\
 &:= (-1 + 2294 + 4 - 02 + 11 + 2)^3 \\
 &:= (1 + 2294 + 4 - 02 - 1 + 12)^3 \\
 &:= (-1 + 2294 + 4 - 02 + 1 + 12)^3 \\
 &:= (1 + 2294 + 4 + 021 - 12)^3 \\
 \mathbf{12296370321} &:= (1 + 2 - 2 + 9 + 6 + 3 - 7 + 0321)^4 \\
 &:= (1 - 2 + 2 + 9 + 6 + 3 - 7 + 0321)^4 \\
 &:= (1 + 2 + 2 + 9 - 6 - 3 + 7 + 0321)^4 \\
 &:= (-1 + 2 - 2 + 9 - 6 + 3 + 7 + 0321)^4 \\
 &:= (-1 - 2 + 2 + 9 - 6 + 3 + 7 + 0321)^4 \\
 &:= (1 + 2 + 2 - 9 + 6 + 3 + 7 + 0321)^4 \\
 &:= (1 + 22 - 9 - 6 - 3 + 7 + 0321)^4 \\
 &:= (1 + 2 + 296 + 3 + 7 + 03 + 21)^4 \\
 &:= (1 - 2 + 29 - 6 - 3 - 7 + 0321)^4 \\
 &:= (-1 + 2 - 2 - 9 + 6 + 370 - 32 - 1)^4 \\
 &:= (-1 - 2 + 2 - 9 + 6 + 370 - 32 - 1)^4 \\
 &:= (1 - 2 - 2 - 9 + 6 + 370 - 32 + 1)^4 \\
 &:= (-12 - 29 + 6 + 370 - 3 + 2 - 1)^4 \\
 &:= (-12 + 2 - 9 + 6 + 370 - 3 - 21)^4 \\
 &:= (-12 + 2 - 9 - 6 + 37 + 0321)^4 \\
 &:= (1 + 229 + 63 + 7 + 032 + 1)^4 \\
 &:= (1 + 229 + 6 + 3 + 70 + 3 + 21)^4 \\
 &:= (1 - 22 + 9 + 6 + 370 - 32 + 1)^4 \\
 &:= (1 + 2 + 296 - 3 + 70 - 32 - 1)^4 \\
 &:= (-1 - 2 + 296 + 3 + 70 - 32 - 1)^4 \\
 &:= (-1 + 2 + 296 - 3 + 70 - 32 + 1)^4 \\
 &:= (-12 + 296 + 3 + 70 - 3 - 21)^4 \\
 &:= (-12 + 296 - 3 + 70 + 3 - 21)^4 \\
 &:= (12 - 2 + 9 + 63 - 70 + 321)^4 \\
 &:= (12 + 2 - 9 - 63 + 70 + 321)^4 \\
 &:= (-12 + 29 + 637 - 0321)^4 \\
 &:= (-12 + 296 + 370 - 321)^4 \\
 \mathbf{12342406231} &:= (-1 + 2342 - 40 + 6 + 2 + 3 - 1)^3 \\
 &:= (1 + 2342 - 40 + 6 - 2 + 3 + 1)^3 \\
 &:= (1 + 2342 - 4 - 06 - 23 + 1)^3 \\
 &:= (-123 + 4 + 2406 + 23 + 1)^3
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 \mathbf{12358435328} &:= (-1 + 2358 - 43 + 5 + 3 - 2 - 8)^3 \\
 &:= (1 + 2358 - 43 + 5 - 3 + 2 - 8)^3 \\
 &:= (-1 + 2358 - 43 - 5 - 3 - 2 + 8)^3 \\
 \mathbf{12374478297} &:= (-1 + 2374 + 4 - 78 - 2 + 9 + 7)^3 \\
 &:= (-1 + 2374 + 47 - 8 - 2 - 97)^3 \\
 &:= (-1 + 2374 - 4 - 78 + 29 - 7)^3 \\
 &:= (1 + 2374 - 47 + 82 - 97)^3 \\
 \mathbf{12390535144} &:= (-1 + 2390 + 5 - 35 - 1 - 44)^3 \\
 \mathbf{12422690496} &:= (1 + 2422 - 6 - 90 + 4 - 9 - 6)^3 \\
 &:= (1 + 2422 - 6 - 9 + 04 - 96)^3 \\
 &:= (-12 + 4 + 2269 + 049 + 6)^3 \\
 &:= (124 - 2 + 2690 - 496)^3 \\
 \mathbf{12444741136} &:= (1 + 244 + 4 + 74 + 1 + 1 + 3 + 6)^4 \\
 &:= (-124 + 447 + 4 - 1 - 1 + 3 + 6)^4 \\
 &:= (1 + 244 + 47 + 4 + 1 + 1 + 36)^4 \\
 &:= (1 + 244 + 4 + 7 + 41 + 1 + 36)^4 \\
 &:= (1 - 24 - 44 - 7 + 411 + 3 - 6)^4 \\
 &:= (-1 - 24 + 4 - 47 + 411 - 3 - 6)^4 \\
 &:= (1 - 24 - 4 - 47 + 411 + 3 - 6)^4 \\
 &:= (-1 - 2 + 4 - 4 + 474 - 1 - 136)^4 \\
 &:= (-1 - 2 - 4 + 4 + 474 - 1 - 136)^4 \\
 &:= (1 + 2 - 4 - 4 + 474 + 1 - 136)^4 \\
 &:= (-124 + 4 + 474 - 11 - 3 - 6)^4 \\
 &:= (-124 + 4 + 474 - 1 - 13 - 6)^4 \\
 &:= (12 + 444 - 7 + 4 - 113 - 6)^4 \\
 &:= (-1 - 24 + 4 + 474 - 113 - 6)^4 \\
 \mathbf{12487168000} &:= (1 + 2487 - 168 + 000)^3 \\
 \mathbf{12503322161} &:= (125 + 033 + 2 + 2161)^3 \\
 &:= (125 + 03 + 32 + 2161)^3 \\
 &:= (1 + 2503 + 32 - 216 + 1)^3 \\
 \mathbf{12519490248} &:= (125 + 1949 + 0248)^3 \\
 \mathbf{12535672267} &:= (1 - 2 + 53 + 5 + 6 - 7 + 2267)^3 \\
 &:= (-1 - 2 + 53 + 5 - 6 + 7 + 2267)^3 \\
 &:= (1 + 2 + 5 + 35 + 6 + 7 + 2267)^3 \\
 &:= (1 - 2 + 5 + 3 + 56 - 7 + 2267)^3 \\
 &:= (-1 + 2 - 5 - 3 + 56 + 7 + 2267)^3 \\
 &:= (125 + 3 - 5 - 67 + 2267)^3 \\
 &:= (-1 + 25 - 35 + 67 + 2267)^3 \\
 \mathbf{12571118641} &:= (1 + 257 + 111864 - 1)^2 \\
 &:= (-1 + 257 + 111864 + 1)^2
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 \mathbf{12594450625} &:= (-1 - 2 - 5 - 94 + 450 - 6 - 2 - 5)^4 \\
 &:= (-125 + 9 + 4 + 450 - 6 - 2 + 5)^4 \\
 &:= (-1 + 259 + 4 + 4 + 50 - 6 + 25)^4 \\
 &:= (1 - 25 - 94 + 450 + 6 + 2 - 5)^4 \\
 &:= (-1 - 2 - 59 + 4 + 450 - 62 + 5)^4 \\
 &:= (1 + 2 - 5 - 94 + 450 + 6 - 25)^4 \\
 &:= (-125 - 9 - 44 + 506 + 2 + 5)^4 \\
 &:= (1 + 259 + 44 + 50 + 6 - 25)^4 \\
 \mathbf{12681938368} &:= (-1 + 2681 + 9 + 3 + 8 - 368)^3 \\
 &:= (12 + 6 + 8 + 1938 + 368)^3 \\
 \mathbf{12745506816} &:= (1 + 274 + 5 - 5 + 068 - 1 - 6)^4 \\
 &:= (1 + 274 - 5 + 5 + 068 - 1 - 6)^4 \\
 &:= (-1 + 274 + 5 - 5 + 068 + 1 - 6)^4 \\
 &:= (-1 + 274 - 5 + 5 + 068 + 1 - 6)^4 \\
 &:= (-1 + 274 - 5 - 5 + 068 - 1 + 6)^4 \\
 &:= (-1 + 274 - 5 + 50 - 6 + 8 + 16)^4 \\
 &:= (1 - 27 + 455 - 06 - 81 - 6)^4 \\
 &:= (-12 - 7 - 455 - 06 + 816)^4 \\
 &:= (-1 - 274 + 550 + 68 - 1 - 6)^4 \\
 &:= (-12 - 7 + 45 - 506 + 816)^4 \\
 \mathbf{12762815625} &:= (-1 + 2 + 7 + 6 + 2 + 81 + 5 + 6 + 2 - 5)^5 \\
 &:= (1 - 2 + 7 + 6 - 2 + 81 + 5 + 6 - 2 + 5)^5 \\
 &:= (1 + 2 + 7 + 6 + 2 + 81 + 5 - 6 + 2 + 5)^5 \\
 &:= (-1 + 2 + 7 + 6 + 2 + 81 - 5 + 6 + 2 + 5)^5 \\
 &:= (1 + 2 + 7 - 6 + 2 + 81 + 5 + 6 + 2 + 5)^5 \\
 &:= (12 + 76 + 2 + 8 - 1 + 5 + 6 + 2 - 5)^5 \\
 &:= (12 + 76 + 2 + 8 + 1 + 5 - 6 + 2 + 5)^5 \\
 &:= (1 + 27 + 62 + 8 - 1 + 5 + 6 + 2 - 5)^5 \\
 &:= (-1 + 27 + 62 + 8 + 1 + 5 + 6 + 2 - 5)^5 \\
 &:= (1 + 27 + 62 + 8 + 1 + 5 - 6 + 2 + 5)^5 \\
 &:= (1 + 27 + 62 + 8 - 1 - 5 + 6 + 2 + 5)^5 \\
 &:= (-1 + 27 + 62 + 8 + 1 - 5 + 6 + 2 + 5)^5 \\
 &:= (1 + 27 + 6 - 2 + 81 + 5 - 6 - 2 - 5)^5 \\
 &:= (-1 + 27 + 6 - 2 + 81 - 5 + 6 - 2 - 5)^5 \\
 &:= (1 + 27 - 6 - 2 + 81 + 5 + 6 - 2 - 5)^5 \\
 &:= (1 + 27 + 6 - 2 + 81 - 5 - 6 - 2 + 5)^5 \\
 &:= (-1 + 27 - 6 + 2 + 81 + 5 - 6 - 2 + 5)^5 \\
 &:= (1 + 27 - 6 - 2 + 81 - 5 + 6 - 2 + 5)^5 \\
 &:= (-1 + 27 - 6 - 2 + 81 + 5 - 6 + 2 + 5)^5
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} &:= (1+27+6+2+8-1+5+62-5)^5 & &:= (12+7-6+2+8+1+56+25)^5 \\ &:= (-1+27+6+2+8+1+5+62-5)^5 & &:= (1-27+62+8-1+5+62-5)^5 \\ &:= (1+27+6+2+8-1-5+62+5)^5 & &:= (-1-27+62+8+1+5+62-5)^5 \\ &:= (-1+27+6+2+8+1-5+62+5)^5 & &:= (1-27+62+8-1-5+62+5)^5 \\ &:= (1+27-6+2+8+1+5+62+5)^5 & &:= (-1-27+62+8+1-5+62+5)^5 \\ &:= (-1+2+76+2+8+15+6+2-5)^5 & &:= (1+27+62-8-1+5-6+25)^5 \\ &:= (1-2+76-2+8+15+6-2+5)^5 & &:= (-1+27+62-8+1+5-6+25)^5 \\ &:= (1+2+76+2+8+15-6+2+5)^5 & &:= (-1+27+62-8-1-5+6+25)^5 \\ &:= (-1-2-7+62-8-1+5+62-5)^5 & &:= (-1-27-6-2-8+156-2-5)^5 \\ &:= (-1-2-7+62-8-1-5+62+5)^5 & &:= (1-2+76+28+15-6-2-5)^5 \\ &:= (1+2+7+62+8+1+5-6+25)^5 & &:= (1+2+76+28-15+6+2+5)^5 \\ &:= (1+2+7+62+8-1-5+6+25)^5 & &:= (1+2+76-28+1+56+2-5)^5 \\ &:= (-1+2+7+62+8+1-5+6+25)^5 & &:= (1-2+76-28-1+56-2+5)^5 \\ &:= (1+2+7+6+28-1+5+62-5)^5 & &:= (-1-2+76-28+1+56-2+5)^5 \\ &:= (-1+2+7+6+28+1+5+62-5)^5 & &:= (1+2+76-2+81-56-2+5)^5 \\ &:= (1+2+7+6+28-1-5+62+5)^5 & &:= (1-2+76+2+81-56-2+5)^5 \\ &:= (-1+2+7+6+28+1-5+62+5)^5 & &:= (1-2+76-2+81-56+2+5)^5 \\ &:= (1+2+7-6+28+1+5+62+5)^5 & &:= (-1-2+76-2-8-15+62-5)^5 \\ &:= (1-2+7+6-2+81-5-6+25)^5 & &:= (-1+2+76+2-8+15-6+25)^5 \\ &:= (-1+2+7-6-2+81+5-6+25)^5 & &:= (1+2+76+2+8-15+6+25)^5 \\ &:= (1+2-7+6-2+81+5-6+25)^5 & &:= (1+2+76+2-8+1+56-25)^5 \\ &:= (-1-2+7-6+2+81+5-6+25)^5 & &:= (1+2+7-62+8+156-2-5)^5 \\ &:= (1-2-7+6+2+81+5-6+25)^5 & &:= (1+2-7-62+8+156+2+5)^5 \\ &:= (1-2+7-6-2+81-5+6+25)^5 & &:= (-1-2-7-6-28+156-2-5)^5 \\ &:= (-1+2-7+6-2+81-5+6+25)^5 & &:= (-1-2-7-6-2-8+156-25)^5 \\ &:= (-1-2-7+6+2+81-5+6+25)^5 & &:= (127-62-8-1+56-2-5)^5 \\ &:= (1+2-7-6-2+81+5+6+25)^5 & &:= (127-6-28+15-6-2+5)^5 \\ &:= (1-2-7-6+2+81+5+6+25)^5 & &:= (127-6+2-81+56+2+5)^5 \\ &:= (127+6-2-8-15-6-2+5)^5 & &:= (127+6-2+8-15+6-25)^5 \\ &:= (127-6-2-8-15+6-2+5)^5 & &:= (-12+76+28-1-5-6+25)^5 \\ &:= (-12+76+28-1+5+6-2+5)^5 & &:= (12+76-2+81+5-62-5)^5 \\ &:= (-12+76-2-8-1-5+62-5)^5 & &:= (12+76-2+81-5-62+5)^5 \\ &:= (12+76+2-8-1+5-6+25)^5 & &:= (12-76+2+8+156-2+5)^5 \\ &:= (12+76-2-8+1-5+6+25)^5 & &:= (12-76-2+8+156+2+5)^5 \\ &:= (-12+76-2+8-1+5+6+25)^5 & &:= (12+7+62+8-15+6+25)^5 \\ &:= (12+7+62+8+15-6+2+5)^5 & &:= (12-7+62-8+15+6+25)^5 \\ &:= (-12-7+62+8+1+56+2-5)^5 & &:= (12-7+62+8-1+56-25)^5 \\ &:= (12+7+6+28-1+56+2-5)^5 & &:= (12+7+62-8+1+56-25)^5 \\ &:= (12+7-6+28+1+56+2+5)^5 & &:= (12+7+6+28-15+62+5)^5 \\ &:= (12+7-6+2+8+15+62+5)^5 & & \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 &:= (-1 + 27 - 62 - 8 + 156 - 2 - 5)^5 \\
 &:= (1 - 27 + 6 - 28 + 156 + 2 - 5)^5 \\
 &:= (1 - 27 + 6 + 2 - 8 + 156 - 25)^5 \\
 &:= (1 - 27 - 6 - 2 + 8 + 156 - 25)^5 \\
 &:= (-1 - 2 + 76 + 28 - 15 - 6 + 25)^5 \\
 &:= (-1 + 2 - 7 - 62 - 8 + 156 + 25)^5 \\
 &:= (-1 + 2 + 7 - 6 - 28 + 156 - 25)^5 \\
 &:= (1 + 2 - 7 + 6 - 28 + 156 - 25)^5 \\
 &:= (127 - 62 + 8 + 1 + 56 - 25)^5 \\
 &:= (12 - 7 - 62 + 81 + 56 + 25)^5 \\
 &:= (1 + 27 - 62 + 8 + 156 - 25)^5 \\
 \mathbf{12796484219} &:= (1279 + 648 + 421 - 9)^3 \\
 \mathbf{12862247607} &:= (-1 - 2 + 86 + 2247 + 6 + 07)^3 \\
 \mathbf{12878723584} &:= (-12 + 8 - 7 + 8 - 7 + 2358 - 4)^3 \\
 &:= (12 - 8 - 7 - 8 - 7 + 2358 + 4)^3 \\
 \mathbf{12897917761} &:= (1 + 289 + 7 + 9 + 17 + 7 + 6 + 1)^4 \\
 &:= (128 + 97 + 91 + 7 + 7 + 6 + 1)^4 \\
 &:= (128 + 9 + 7 + 9 + 177 + 6 + 1)^4 \\
 &:= (-1 + 289 + 7 - 9 - 17 + 7 + 61)^4 \\
 &:= (1 - 2 + 89 + 79 + 177 - 6 - 1)^4 \\
 &:= (-1 - 2 + 89 + 79 + 177 - 6 + 1)^4 \\
 &:= (1 + 2 + 8 + 97 + 91 + 77 + 61)^4 \\
 &:= (1 + 2 + 8 + 97 - 9 + 177 + 61)^4 \\
 &:= (-1 + 2 - 8 + 97 + 9 + 177 + 61)^4 \\
 &:= (1 + 2 + 8 + 9 + 79 + 177 + 61)^4 \\
 &:= (128 - 9 + 79 + 1 + 77 + 61)^4 \\
 &:= (12 + 89 + 7 + 91 + 77 + 61)^4 \\
 &:= (12 + 89 + 7 - 9 + 177 + 61)^4 \\
 &:= (1 + 28 - 9 + 79 + 177 + 61)^4 \\
 \mathbf{12928235923} &:= (12 - 9 - 2 - 8 + 2359 - 2 - 3)^3 \\
 &:= (-12 - 9 + 2 + 8 + 2359 + 2 - 3)^3 \\
 &:= (-12 + 9 - 2 - 8 + 2359 - 2 + 3)^3 \\
 &:= (12 + 9 - 28 + 2359 - 2 - 3)^3 \\
 &:= (12 + 9 - 2 - 8 + 2359 - 23)^3 \\
 \mathbf{12961139409} &:= (12 - 96 + 113940 - 9)^2 \\
 \mathbf{13051691536} &:= (1 + 305 + 16 + 9 - 1 + 5 - 3 + 6)^4 \\
 &:= (-1 + 305 + 16 + 9 + 1 + 5 - 3 + 6)^4 \\
 &:= (1 + 305 - 1 + 6 + 9 + 15 - 3 + 6)^4 \\
 &:= (-1 + 305 + 1 + 6 + 9 + 15 - 3 + 6)^4 \\
 &:= (1 + 305 + 1 - 6 - 9 - 1 + 53 - 6)^4 \\
 &:= (1 + 305 - 1 - 6 - 9 + 1 + 53 - 6)^4 \\
 &:= (-1 + 305 + 1 - 6 - 9 + 1 + 53 - 6)^4 \\
 &:= (1 + 305 - 1 - 6 + 9 - 1 - 5 + 36)^4 \\
 &:= (-1 + 305 + 1 - 6 + 9 - 1 - 5 + 36)^4 \\
 &:= (-1 + 305 - 1 - 6 + 9 + 1 - 5 + 36)^4 \\
 &:= (-1 + 305 - 16 + 91 - 5 - 36)^4 \\
 &:= (1305 - 16 - 915 - 36)^4 \\
 \mathbf{13060694016} &:= (-1 - 3 + 06 + 06 + 9 - 4 - 01 - 6)^{13} \\
 &:= (1 + 3 + 06 + 06 - 9 + 4 + 01 - 6)^{13} \\
 &:= (1 - 3 + 06 - 06 + 9 + 4 + 01 - 6)^{13} \\
 &:= (1 - 3 - 06 + 06 + 9 + 4 + 01 - 6)^{13} \\
 &:= (-1 + 3 + 06 + 06 - 9 - 4 - 01 + 6)^{13} \\
 &:= (-1 - 3 + 06 - 06 + 9 - 4 - 01 + 6)^{13} \\
 &:= (-1 - 3 - 06 + 06 + 9 - 4 - 01 + 6)^{13} \\
 &:= (1 + 3 + 06 - 06 - 9 + 4 + 01 + 6)^{13} \\
 &:= (1 + 3 - 06 + 06 - 9 + 4 + 01 + 6)^{13} \\
 &:= (1 - 3 - 06 - 06 + 9 + 4 + 01 + 6)^{13} \\
 &:= (-1 + 30 - 6 - 06 + 9 - 4 - 016)^{13} \\
 &:= (1 - 3 - 060 + 69 + 4 + 01 - 6)^{13} \\
 &:= (-1 - 3 - 060 + 69 - 4 - 01 + 6)^{13} \\
 &:= (1 + 3 + 060 - 69 + 4 + 01 + 6)^{13} \\
 &:= (-1 - 3 + 060 + 6 - 9 - 40 - 1 - 6)^{13} \\
 &:= (-1 - 3 + 060 - 6 - 9 - 40 - 1 + 6)^{13} \\
 &:= (1 + 3 - 060 + 6 + 9 + 40 + 1 + 6)^{13} \\
 &:= (1 - 30 - 60 + 6 + 94 + 01 - 6)^{13} \\
 &:= (-1 + 30 + 60 + 6 - 94 - 01 + 6)^{13} \\
 &:= (1 - 30 - 60 - 6 + 94 + 01 + 6)^{13} \\
 &:= (-1 - 30 + 60 + 6 - 9 - 4 - 016)^{13} \\
 &:= (1 + 30 - 60 + 6 + 9 + 4 + 016)^{13} \\
 &:= (1 - 30 - 6 - 06 - 9 + 40 + 16)^{13} \\
 &:= (-13 + 060 + 6 + 9 - 40 - 16)^{13} \\
 &:= (13 - 060 + 6 - 9 + 40 + 16)^{13} \\
 &:= (-13 + 06 + 069 - 40 - 16)^{13} \\
 &:= (13 + 06 - 069 + 40 + 16)^{13} \\
 \mathbf{13094193293} &:= (-1 - 3 - 0941 + 9 + 3293)^3 \\
 \mathbf{13141183225} &:= (-1 + 31411 + 83225)^2 \\
 \mathbf{13206836241} &:= (-1 + 320 + 6 + 8 + 3 + 6 + 2 - 4 - 1)^4 \\
 &:= (1 + 320 + 6 + 8 - 3 + 6 - 2 + 4 - 1)^4 \\
 &:= (1 + 320 + 6 + 8 + 3 + 6 - 2 - 4 + 1)^4 \\
 &:= (-1 + 320 + 6 + 8 - 3 + 6 - 2 + 4 + 1)^4
 \end{aligned}$$

$:= (1 + 320 + 6 + 8 + 3 - 6 + 2 + 4 + 1)^4$	$:= (-1 + 3 + 3 + 8 - 2 + 2 + 5 + 5 + 77 + 6)^5$
$:= (1 + 320 - 6 + 8 + 3 + 6 + 2 + 4 + 1)^4$	$:= (1 + 3 - 3 + 8 + 2 + 2 + 5 + 5 + 77 + 6)^5$
$:= (1 - 3 - 2 - 06 - 8 + 362 - 4 - 1)^4$	$:= (1 - 3 + 3 + 8 + 2 + 2 + 5 + 5 + 77 + 6)^5$
$:= (-1 - 3 - 2 - 06 - 8 + 362 - 4 + 1)^4$	$:= (-1 + 3 + 3 + 8 + 2 - 2 + 5 + 5 + 7 + 76)^5$
$:= (1 + 320 + 6 - 8 + 3 - 6 + 24 - 1)^4$	$:= (-1 + 3 + 3 + 8 - 2 + 2 + 5 + 5 + 7 + 76)^5$
$:= (1 + 320 - 6 - 8 + 3 + 6 + 24 - 1)^4$	$:= (1 + 3 - 3 + 8 + 2 + 2 + 5 + 5 + 7 + 76)^5$
$:= (1 + 320 - 6 + 8 - 3 - 6 + 24 + 1)^4$	$:= (1 - 3 + 3 + 8 + 2 + 2 + 5 + 5 + 7 + 76)^5$
$:= (-1 + 320 + 6 - 8 + 3 - 6 + 24 + 1)^4$	$:= (13 + 3 + 82 + 2 + 5 - 5 + 7 - 7 + 6)^5$
$:= (-1 + 320 - 6 - 8 + 3 + 6 + 24 + 1)^4$	$:= (13 + 3 + 82 + 2 - 5 + 5 + 7 - 7 + 6)^5$
$:= (-1 + 320 - 6 - 8 - 3 - 6 + 2 + 41)^4$	$:= (13 - 3 + 82 - 2 + 5 + 5 + 7 - 7 + 6)^5$
$:= (1 + 3 - 20 + 6 - 8 + 362 - 4 - 1)^4$	$:= (13 + 3 + 82 + 2 + 5 - 5 - 7 + 7 + 6)^5$
$:= (-1 - 3 - 20 + 6 - 8 + 362 + 4 - 1)^4$	$:= (13 + 3 + 82 + 2 - 5 + 5 - 7 + 7 + 6)^5$
$:= (-1 + 3 - 20 + 6 - 8 + 362 - 4 + 1)^4$	$:= (13 - 3 + 82 - 2 + 5 + 5 - 7 + 7 + 6)^5$
$:= (1 - 3 - 20 - 6 + 8 + 362 - 4 + 1)^4$	$:= (13 + 3 + 82 - 2 - 5 - 5 + 7 + 7 + 6)^5$
$:= (-1 + 3 + 2 + 06 + 8 + 362 - 41)^4$	$:= (-1 + 33 + 82 + 2 + 5 + 5 - 7 - 7 - 6)^5$
$:= (13 + 2 + 06 + 83 - 6 + 241)^4$	$:= (-1 + 33 + 82 - 2 + 5 - 5 + 7 - 7 - 6)^5$
$:= (13 + 2 - 06 + 83 + 6 + 241)^4$	$:= (-1 + 33 + 82 - 2 - 5 + 5 + 7 - 7 - 6)^5$
$:= (-1 + 320 + 68 - 3 - 6 + 2 - 41)^4$	$:= (-1 + 33 + 82 - 2 + 5 - 5 - 7 + 7 - 6)^5$
$:= (1 + 320 - 6 + 83 - 62 + 4 - 1)^4$	$:= (-1 + 33 + 82 - 2 - 5 + 5 - 7 + 7 - 6)^5$
$:= (-1 + 320 - 6 + 83 - 62 + 4 + 1)^4$	$:= (1 + 33 + 82 - 2 + 5 - 5 - 7 - 7 + 6)^5$
$:= (-1 + 320 - 6 + 8 - 3 + 62 - 41)^4$	$:= (1 + 33 + 82 - 2 - 5 + 5 - 7 - 7 + 6)^5$
$:= (1 + 32 + 068 + 3 - 6 + 241)^4$	$:= (1 + 3 - 3 + 8 + 22 + 55 + 7 + 7 + 6)^5$
$:= (-1 - 3 + 20 - 6 + 8 + 362 - 41)^4$	$:= (1 - 3 + 3 + 8 + 22 + 55 + 7 + 7 + 6)^5$
$:= (-1 + 3 + 2 - 068 + 362 + 41)^4$	$:= (1 + 3 - 3 + 8 + 22 + 5 + 57 + 7 + 6)^5$
$:= (-1 - 3 - 2 + 068 + 36 + 241)^4$	$:= (1 - 3 + 3 + 8 + 22 + 5 + 57 + 7 + 6)^5$
$:= (132 - 06 + 8 - 36 + 241)^4$	$:= (-1 + 3 + 3 + 8 + 22 + 5 - 5 + 77 - 6)^5$
$:= (13 + 206 + 83 - 6 + 2 + 41)^4$	$:= (-1 + 3 + 3 + 8 + 22 - 5 + 5 + 77 - 6)^5$
$:= (13 + 20 + 68 + 3 - 6 + 241)^4$	$:= (1 - 3 - 3 + 8 + 22 + 5 + 5 + 77 - 6)^5$
$:= (-132 + 068 + 362 + 41)^4$	$:= (-1 - 3 - 3 + 8 + 22 + 5 - 5 + 77 + 6)^5$
13211204544 $:= (-1 + 321 - 1 + 2045 + 4 - 4)^3$	$:= (-1 - 3 - 3 + 8 + 22 - 5 + 5 + 77 + 6)^5$
$:= (-1 + 321 - 1 + 2045 - 4 + 4)^3$	$:= (-1 + 3 - 3 - 8 + 22 + 5 + 5 + 77 + 6)^5$
13227977125 $:= (13 + 2279 + 77 - 1 + 2 - 5)^3$	$:= (-1 - 3 + 3 - 8 + 22 + 5 + 5 + 77 + 6)^5$
$:= (-1 + 3 + 2279 + 77 + 12 - 5)^3$	$:= (1 + 3 + 3 + 8 + 22 + 5 - 5 - 7 + 76)^5$
13244763896 $:= (1 + 3 + 2447 + 6 - 3 + 8 - 96)^3$	$:= (1 + 3 + 3 + 8 + 22 - 5 + 5 - 7 + 76)^5$
$:= (1 - 3 + 2447 + 6 + 3 + 8 - 96)^3$	$:= (-1 - 3 - 3 + 8 + 22 + 5 - 5 + 7 + 76)^5$
$:= (-13 + 2447 - 63 - 8 + 9 - 6)^3$	$:= (-1 - 3 - 3 + 8 + 22 - 5 + 5 + 7 + 76)^5$
13363360000 $:= (13 - 3 - 6 + 336 + 0000)^4$	$:= (-1 + 3 - 3 - 8 + 22 + 5 + 5 + 7 + 76)^5$
$:= (13 + 363 - 36 + 0000)^4$	$:= (-1 - 3 + 3 - 8 + 22 + 5 + 5 + 7 + 76)^5$
$:= (13 - 36 + 3 + 360 + 000)^4$	$:= (-1 + 3 + 3 + 8 - 2 + 25 + 57 + 7 + 6)^5$
13382255776 $:= (-1 + 3 + 3 + 8 + 2 - 2 + 5 + 5 + 77 + 6)^5$	$:= (1 + 3 - 3 + 8 + 2 + 25 + 57 + 7 + 6)^5$

$$\begin{aligned} &:= (1 - 3 + 3 + 8 + 2 + 25 + 57 + 7 + 6)^5 & &:= (-13 + 38 + 22 - 5 - 5 - 7 + 76)^5 \\ &:= (-1 + 3 + 3 + 8 + 2 + 25 - 5 + 77 - 6)^5 & &:= (-13 + 38 - 2 + 25 + 57 + 7 - 6)^5 \\ &:= (-1 + 3 - 3 + 8 - 2 + 25 + 5 + 77 - 6)^5 & &:= (13 + 38 + 2 - 25 - 5 + 77 + 6)^5 \\ &:= (-1 - 3 + 3 + 8 - 2 + 25 + 5 + 77 - 6)^5 & &:= (13 + 38 + 2 - 25 - 5 + 7 + 76)^5 \\ &:= (1 - 3 - 3 + 8 + 2 + 25 + 5 + 77 - 6)^5 & &:= (13 - 3 + 82 - 2 - 55 + 77 - 6)^5 \\ &:= (-1 - 3 - 3 + 8 + 2 + 25 - 5 + 77 + 6)^5 & &:= (13 - 3 - 8 - 22 + 55 + 77 - 6)^5 \\ &:= (-1 + 3 - 3 - 8 + 2 + 25 + 5 + 77 + 6)^5 & &:= (1 + 338 + 2 - 255 + 7 + 7 + 6)^5 \\ &:= (-1 - 3 + 3 - 8 + 2 + 25 + 5 + 77 + 6)^5 & &:= (-1 - 33 - 8 + 22 + 55 + 77 - 6)^5 \\ &:= (1 + 3 + 3 + 8 + 2 + 25 - 5 - 7 + 76)^5 & &:= (1 - 33 - 8 + 22 + 55 - 7 + 76)^5 \\ &:= (1 + 3 - 3 + 8 - 2 + 25 + 5 - 7 + 76)^5 & &:= (-1 - 3 - 38 + 22 + 55 + 77 - 6)^5 \\ &:= (1 - 3 + 3 + 8 - 2 + 25 + 5 - 7 + 76)^5 & &:= (1 - 3 - 38 + 22 + 55 - 7 + 76)^5 \\ &:= (-1 - 3 - 3 + 8 + 2 + 25 - 5 + 7 + 76)^5 & &:= (-13 + 382 - 255 - 7 - 7 + 6)^5 \\ &:= (-1 + 3 - 3 - 8 + 2 + 25 + 5 + 7 + 76)^5 & &:= (13 + 3 - 82 + 255 - 77 - 6)^5 \\ &:= (-1 - 3 + 3 - 8 + 2 + 25 + 5 + 7 + 76)^5 & &:= (13 + 3 - 82 + 255 - 7 - 76)^5 \\ &:= (133 + 8 + 2 - 2 - 55 + 7 + 7 + 6)^5 & &:= (-1 + 3 + 3 + 822 + 55 - 776)^5 \\ &:= (133 + 8 - 2 + 2 - 55 + 7 + 7 + 6)^5 & & \mathbf{13413413376} := (-1341 + 341 + 3376)^3 \\ &:= (133 + 8 + 2 + 2 + 5 - 57 + 7 + 6)^5 & & \mathbf{13430356633} := (1 + 3 + 4 + 3035 - 663 - 3)^3 \\ &:= (13 + 38 + 2 + 2 - 5 + 57 - 7 + 6)^5 & & := (1 - 3 + 4 + 3035 - 663 + 3)^3 \\ &:= (-13 + 38 + 2 - 2 + 5 + 5 + 77 - 6)^5 & & \mathbf{13464285939} := (-1 - 3 - 464 + 2859 - 3 - 9)^3 \\ &:= (-13 + 38 - 2 + 2 + 5 + 5 + 77 - 6)^5 & & \mathbf{13492928512} := (-1 + 3 + 4 + 9 + 2 + 9 + 2 + 8 - 5 - 1 - 2)^7 \\ &:= (13 + 38 - 2 - 2 - 5 - 5 - 7 + 76)^5 & & := (1 + 3 - 4 + 9 + 2 + 9 - 2 + 8 + 5 - 1 - 2)^7 \\ &:= (13 - 3 + 82 + 25 - 5 + 7 - 7 - 6)^5 & & := (-1 - 3 + 4 + 9 + 2 + 9 - 2 + 8 + 5 - 1 - 2)^7 \\ &:= (13 - 3 + 82 + 25 - 5 - 7 + 7 - 6)^5 & & := (1 + 3 - 4 + 9 - 2 + 9 + 2 + 8 + 5 - 1 - 2)^7 \\ &:= (-13 - 3 + 82 + 25 - 5 + 7 + 7 + 6)^5 & & := (-1 - 3 + 4 + 9 - 2 + 9 + 2 + 8 + 5 - 1 - 2)^7 \\ &:= (-13 - 3 - 8 + 2 + 2 + 55 + 77 - 6)^5 & & := (1 + 3 + 4 + 9 + 2 + 9 - 2 + 8 - 5 + 1 - 2)^7 \\ &:= (-13 + 3 - 8 + 2 - 2 + 55 - 7 + 76)^5 & & := (1 + 3 + 4 + 9 - 2 + 9 + 2 + 8 - 5 + 1 - 2)^7 \\ &:= (-13 + 3 - 8 - 2 + 2 + 55 - 7 + 76)^5 & & := (1 - 3 + 4 + 9 - 2 + 9 - 2 + 8 + 5 + 1 - 2)^7 \\ &:= (-13 + 3 - 8 - 2 - 2 - 5 + 57 + 76)^5 & & := (-1 + 3 - 4 + 9 + 2 + 9 - 2 + 8 + 5 + 1 - 2)^7 \\ &:= (1 + 33 + 82 - 25 - 5 + 7 + 7 + 6)^5 & & := (-1 + 3 - 4 + 9 - 2 + 9 + 2 + 8 + 5 + 1 - 2)^7 \\ &:= (1 - 33 + 8 + 2 + 2 + 55 + 77 - 6)^5 & & := (1 - 3 - 4 + 9 + 2 + 9 + 2 + 8 + 5 + 1 - 2)^7 \\ &:= (-1 - 33 + 8 + 2 + 2 - 5 + 57 + 76)^5 & & := (-1 + 3 + 4 + 9 + 2 + 9 - 2 + 8 - 5 - 1 + 2)^7 \\ &:= (-1 + 3 - 38 + 2 + 2 + 55 + 77 + 6)^5 & & := (-1 + 3 + 4 + 9 - 2 + 9 + 2 + 8 - 5 - 1 + 2)^7 \\ &:= (-1 + 3 - 38 + 2 + 2 + 55 + 7 + 76)^5 & & := (1 - 3 + 4 + 9 + 2 + 9 + 2 + 8 - 5 - 1 + 2)^7 \\ &:= (-1 + 3 - 38 + 2 + 2 + 5 + 57 + 76)^5 & & := (1 + 3 + 4 + 9 + 2 + 9 + 2 - 8 + 5 - 1 + 2)^7 \\ &:= (-1 + 3 + 3 + 82 - 25 + 57 - 7 - 6)^5 & & := (1 + 3 - 4 + 9 - 2 + 9 - 2 + 8 + 5 - 1 + 2)^7 \\ &:= (-1 - 3 - 3 + 82 - 25 + 57 - 7 + 6)^5 & & := (-1 - 3 + 4 + 9 - 2 + 9 - 2 + 8 + 5 - 1 + 2)^7 \\ &:= (133 - 82 + 2 - 5 + 57 + 7 - 6)^5 & & := (-1 - 3 - 4 + 9 + 2 + 9 + 2 + 8 + 5 - 1 + 2)^7 \\ &:= (-133 - 8 - 2 + 255 + 7 - 7 - 6)^5 & & := (1 + 3 + 4 + 9 - 2 + 9 - 2 + 8 - 5 + 1 + 2)^7 \\ &:= (-133 - 8 - 2 + 255 - 7 + 7 - 6)^5 & & := (1 + 3 - 4 + 9 + 2 + 9 + 2 + 8 - 5 + 1 + 2)^7 \\ &:= (133 + 8 - 2 + 25 - 57 - 7 + 6)^5 & & := (-1 - 3 + 4 + 9 + 2 + 9 + 2 + 8 - 5 + 1 + 2)^7 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} &:= (-1+3+4+9+2+9+2-8+5+1+2)^7 \\ &:= (-1+3-4+9-2+9-2+8+5+1+2)^7 \\ &:= (1-3-4+9+2+9-2+8+5+1+2)^7 \\ &:= (1+3+4+9+2-9+2+8+5+1+2)^7 \\ &:= (1-3-4+9-2+9+2+8+5+1+2)^7 \\ &:= (1+3+4-9+2+9+2+8+5+1+2)^7 \\ &:= (1+3+49+2-9-2-8-5-1-2)^7 \\ &:= (1+3+49-2-9+2-8-5-1-2)^7 \\ &:= (1-3+49-2-9-2-8+5-1-2)^7 \\ &:= (-1+3+49+2-9-2-8-5+1-2)^7 \\ &:= (-1+3+49-2-9+2-8-5+1-2)^7 \\ &:= (1-3+49+2-9+2-8-5+1-2)^7 \\ &:= (-1-3+49-2-9-2-8+5+1-2)^7 \\ &:= (1+3+49-2-9-2-8-5-1+2)^7 \\ &:= (-1-3+49+2-9+2-8-5-1+2)^7 \\ &:= (-1+3+49-2-9-2-8-5+1+2)^7 \\ &:= (1-3+49+2-9-2-8-5+1+2)^7 \\ &:= (1-3+49-2-9+2-8-5+1+2)^7 \\ &:= (1+3+4+9+29-2-8-5-1-2)^7 \\ &:= (-1-3-4+9+29-2+8-5-1-2)^7 \\ &:= (-1+3+4-9+29+2+8-5-1-2)^7 \\ &:= (-1+3-4+9+29-2-8+5-1-2)^7 \\ &:= (1-3-4+9+29+2-8+5-1-2)^7 \\ &:= (1+3-4-9+29-2+8+5-1-2)^7 \\ &:= (-1-3+4-9+29-2+8+5-1-2)^7 \\ &:= (-1+3+4+9+29-2-8-5+1-2)^7 \\ &:= (1-3+4+9+29+2-8-5+1-2)^7 \\ &:= (1+3+4-9+29-2+8-5+1-2)^7 \\ &:= (-1-3-4+9+29+2-8+5+1-2)^7 \\ &:= (-1+3-4-9+29-2+8+5+1-2)^7 \\ &:= (1-3-4-9+29+2+8+5+1-2)^7 \\ &:= (1+3-4+9+29+2-8-5-1+2)^7 \\ &:= (-1-3+4+9+29+2-8-5-1+2)^7 \\ &:= (-1+3+4-9+29-2+8-5-1+2)^7 \\ &:= (1-3+4-9+29+2+8-5-1+2)^7 \\ &:= (1-3-4+9+29-2-8+5-1+2)^7 \\ &:= (1+3+4-9+29+2-8+5-1+2)^7 \\ &:= (-1-3-4-9+29+2+8+5-1+2)^7 \\ &:= (1-3+4+9+29-2-8-5+1+2)^7 \\ &:= (-1+3-4+9+29+2-8-5+1+2)^7 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} &:= (1+3-4-9+29+2+8-5+1+2)^7 \\ &:= (-1-3+4-9+29+2+8-5+1+2)^7 \\ &:= (-1-3-4+9+29-2-8+5+1+2)^7 \\ &:= (-1+3+4-9+29+2-8+5+1+2)^7 \\ &:= (1-3-4-9+29-2+8+5+1+2)^7 \\ &:= (-1+3+4+9+2-9+28-5-1-2)^7 \\ &:= (-1-3-4+9-2+9+28-5-1-2)^7 \\ &:= (-1+3+4-9+2+9+28-5-1-2)^7 \\ &:= (1+3-4+9-2-9+28+5-1-2)^7 \\ &:= (-1-3+4+9-2-9+28+5-1-2)^7 \\ &:= (1+3-4-9-2+9+28+5-1-2)^7 \\ &:= (-1-3+4-9-2+9+28+5-1-2)^7 \\ &:= (1+3+4+9-2-9+28-5+1-2)^7 \\ &:= (1+3+4-9-2+9+28-5+1-2)^7 \\ &:= (-1+3-4+9-2-9+28+5+1-2)^7 \\ &:= (1-3-4+9+2-9+28+5+1-2)^7 \\ &:= (-1+3-4-9-2+9+28+5+1-2)^7 \\ &:= (1-3-4-9+2+9+28+5+1-2)^7 \\ &:= (-1+3+4+9-2-9+28-5-1+2)^7 \\ &:= (1-3+4+9+2-9+28-5-1+2)^7 \\ &:= (-1+3+4-9-2+9+28-5-1+2)^7 \\ &:= (1-3+4-9+2+9+28-5-1+2)^7 \\ &:= (-1-3-4+9+2-9+28+5-1+2)^7 \\ &:= (-1-3-4-9+2+9+28+5-1+2)^7 \\ &:= (1+3-4+9+2-9+28-5+1+2)^7 \\ &:= (-1-3+4+9+2-9+28-5+1+2)^7 \\ &:= (1+3-4-9+2+9+28-5+1+2)^7 \\ &:= (-1-3+4-9+2+9+28-5+1+2)^7 \\ &:= (1-3-4+9-2-9+28+5+1+2)^7 \\ &:= (1+3+4-9+2-9+28+5+1+2)^7 \\ &:= (1-3-4-9-2+9+28+5+1+2)^7 \\ &:= (13-4-9-2-9-2-8+51-2)^7 \\ &:= (-13+4+9-2-9-2-8+51-2)^7 \\ &:= (-13+4-9-2+9-2-8+51-2)^7 \\ &:= (-13-4+9+2-9+2-8+51-2)^7 \\ &:= (-13-4-9+2+9+2-8+51-2)^7 \\ &:= (-13-4+9+2-9-2-8+51+2)^7 \\ &:= (-13-4-9+2+9-2-8+51+2)^7 \\ &:= (-13-4+9-2-9+2-8+51+2)^7 \\ &:= (-13-4-9-2+9+2-8+51+2)^7 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} &:= (13-4+9+2+9-2+8+5-12)^7 & &:= (-1+3-49+2-9-2+85+1-2)^7 \\ &:= (13-4+9-2+9+2+8+5-12)^7 & &:= (-1+3-49-2-9+2+85+1-2)^7 \\ &:= (13+4+9-2-9-2+8-5+12)^7 & &:= (1-3-49+2-9+2+85+1-2)^7 \\ &:= (13+4-9-2+9-2+8-5+12)^7 & &:= (1+3-49-2-9-2+85-1+2)^7 \\ &:= (13-4+9+2-9+2+8-5+12)^7 & &:= (-1-3-49+2-9+2+85-1+2)^7 \\ &:= (13-4-9+2+9+2+8-5+12)^7 & &:= (-1+3-49-2-9-2+85+1+2)^7 \\ &:= (-13+4+9+2+9+2+8-5+12)^7 & &:= (1-3-49+2-9-2+85+1+2)^7 \\ &:= (13+4-9+2-9+2+8+5+12)^7 & &:= (1-3-49-2-9+2+85+1+2)^7 \\ &:= (-1-34+9+2+9+2-8+51-2)^7 & &:= (1+3+4+92-9-2-8-51-2)^7 \\ &:= (1-34+9+2-9+2+8+51-2)^7 & &:= (-1-3-4+92-9-2+8-51-2)^7 \\ &:= (1-34-9+2+9+2+8+51-2)^7 & &:= (1+3-4+92-9+2-8-51+2)^7 \\ &:= (-1-34+9+2+9-2-8+51+2)^7 & &:= (-1-3+4+92-9+2-8-51+2)^7 \\ &:= (-1-34+9-2+9+2-8+51+2)^7 & &:= (1+3+4-9-2+92-8-51-2)^7 \\ &:= (1-34+9+2-9-2+8+51+2)^7 & &:= (-1-3-4-9-2+92+8-51-2)^7 \\ &:= (1-34-9+2+9-2+8+51+2)^7 & &:= (1+3-4-9+2+92-8-51+2)^7 \\ &:= (1-34+9-2-9+2+8+51+2)^7 & &:= (-1-3+4-9+2+92-8-51+2)^7 \\ &:= (1-34-9-2+9+2+8+51+2)^7 & &:= (134-9+2-9-2-85-1-2)^7 \\ &:= (1+34+9+2+9-2-8-5-12)^7 & &:= (134-9-2-9+2-85-1-2)^7 \\ &:= (1+34+9-2+9+2-8-5-12)^7 & &:= (134-9-2-9-2-85-1+2)^7 \\ &:= (-1+34+9+2-9+2+8-5-12)^7 & &:= (-13-49-2+92+8-5-1-2)^7 \\ &:= (-1+34-9+2+9+2+8-5-12)^7 & &:= (-13-49+2+92-8+5+1-2)^7 \\ &:= (-1+34+9-2-9-2-8-5+12)^7 & &:= (-13-49-2+92-8+5+1+2)^7 \\ &:= (-1+34-9-2+9-2-8-5+12)^7 & &:= (13+49+2-9-2-8-5-12)^7 \\ &:= (1+34-9-2-9-2+8-5+12)^7 & &:= (13+49-2-9+2-8-5-12)^7 \\ &:= (-1+34-9+2-9+2-8+5+12)^7 & &:= (-13+49+2-9-2+8+5-12)^7 \\ &:= (-1-3+49-29+2+8+5-1-2)^7 & &:= (-13+49-2-9+2+8+5-12)^7 \\ &:= (1+3+49-29+2+8-5+1-2)^7 & &:= (13+4+92+9-2-85-1-2)^7 \\ &:= (1-3+49-29-2+8+5+1-2)^7 & &:= (13-4+92+9+2-85-1+2)^7 \\ &:= (-1+3+49-29+2+8-5-1+2)^7 & &:= (13-4+9-29-2-8+51-2)^7 \\ &:= (-1-3+49-29-2+8+5-1+2)^7 & &:= (13+4+9+29-2-8-5-12)^7 \\ &:= (1+3+49-29-2+8-5+1+2)^7 & &:= (13-4-9+29-2+8+5-12)^7 \\ &:= (1+3+49+2+9-28-5-1-2)^7 & &:= (-13+4+9+29-2+8+5-12)^7 \\ &:= (1-3+49-2+9-28+5-1-2)^7 & &:= (-13+4-9+29+2+8-5+12)^7 \\ &:= (-1+3+49+2+9-28-5+1-2)^7 & &:= (-13-4+9+29-2-8+5+12)^7 \\ &:= (-1-3+49-2+9-28+5+1-2)^7 & &:= (13+4+9-2+92-85-1-2)^7 \\ &:= (1+3+49-2+9-28-5-1+2)^7 & &:= (13-4+9+2+92-85-1+2)^7 \\ &:= (-1+3+49-2+9-28-5+1+2)^7 & &:= (13-4+9-2-9-28+51-2)^7 \\ &:= (1-3+49+2+9-28-5+1+2)^7 & &:= (13-4-9-2+9-28+51-2)^7 \\ &:= (1+3-49+2-9-2+85-1-2)^7 & &:= (-13+4+9-2+9-28+51-2)^7 \\ &:= (1+3-49-2-9+2+85-1-2)^7 & &:= (-13-4+9+2+9-28+51+2)^7 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 &:= (13 - 4 + 9 - 2 - 9 + 28 + 5 - 12)^7 \\
 &:= (13 - 4 - 9 - 2 + 9 + 28 + 5 - 12)^7 \\
 &:= (-13 + 4 + 9 - 2 + 9 + 28 + 5 - 12)^7 \\
 &:= (13 - 4 - 9 + 2 - 9 + 28 - 5 + 12)^7 \\
 &:= (-13 + 4 + 9 + 2 - 9 + 28 - 5 + 12)^7 \\
 &:= (-13 + 4 - 9 + 2 + 9 + 28 - 5 + 12)^7 \\
 &:= (1 - 34 + 92 - 9 - 28 + 5 - 1 + 2)^7 \\
 &:= (-1 - 34 + 92 - 9 - 28 + 5 + 1 + 2)^7 \\
 &:= (1 + 34 + 92 - 9 - 2 - 85 - 1 - 2)^7 \\
 &:= (-1 + 34 + 92 - 9 - 2 - 85 + 1 - 2)^7 \\
 &:= (-1 + 34 + 9 + 29 + 2 + 8 - 51 - 2)^7 \\
 &:= (-1 - 34 - 9 + 29 + 2 - 8 + 51 - 2)^7 \\
 &:= (-1 + 34 + 9 + 29 - 2 + 8 - 51 + 2)^7 \\
 &:= (-1 - 34 - 9 + 29 - 2 - 8 + 51 + 2)^7 \\
 &:= (1 + 34 - 9 + 29 - 2 - 8 - 5 - 12)^7 \\
 &:= (1 + 34 + 9 - 29 - 2 + 8 - 5 + 12)^7 \\
 &:= (1 - 34 + 9 + 29 - 2 + 8 + 5 + 12)^7 \\
 &:= (1 + 34 - 9 - 2 + 92 - 85 - 1 - 2)^7 \\
 &:= (-1 + 34 - 9 - 2 + 92 - 85 + 1 - 2)^7 \\
 &:= (-1 + 34 + 9 + 2 + 9 + 28 - 51 - 2)^7 \\
 &:= (1 - 34 - 9 + 2 - 9 + 28 + 51 - 2)^7 \\
 &:= (-1 + 34 + 9 - 2 + 9 + 28 - 51 + 2)^7 \\
 &:= (1 - 34 - 9 - 2 - 9 + 28 + 51 + 2)^7 \\
 &:= (-1 + 34 - 9 + 2 - 9 + 28 - 5 - 12)^7 \\
 &:= (-1 + 34 + 9 - 2 + 9 - 28 - 5 + 12)^7 \\
 &:= (1 - 34 + 9 - 2 + 9 + 28 + 5 + 12)^7 \\
 &:= (-1 - 3 - 49 - 2 + 92 + 8 - 5 - 12)^7 \\
 &:= (-1 + 3 - 49 - 2 + 92 - 8 + 5 - 12)^7 \\
 &:= (1 - 3 - 49 + 2 + 92 - 8 + 5 - 12)^7 \\
 &:= (1 + 3 + 4 + 92 + 9 - 28 - 51 - 2)^7 \\
 &:= (1 - 3 + 4 + 92 + 9 - 2 - 85 + 12)^7 \\
 &:= (-1 + 3 - 4 + 92 + 9 + 2 - 85 + 12)^7 \\
 &:= (1 - 3 + 4 + 9 - 2 + 92 - 85 + 12)^7 \\
 &:= (-1 + 3 - 4 + 9 + 2 + 92 - 85 + 12)^7 \\
 &:= (134 - 92 + 9 + 2 - 8 - 5 - 12)^7 \\
 &:= (134 + 9 - 29 + 2 - 85 - 1 - 2)^7 \\
 &:= (134 + 9 - 29 - 2 - 85 - 1 + 2)^7 \\
 &:= (134 + 9 + 2 - 92 - 8 - 5 - 12)^7 \\
 &:= (13 + 49 + 29 - 2 - 8 - 51 - 2)^7 \\
 &:= (-13 + 49 + 2 - 92 + 85 - 1 - 2)^7
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 &:= (-13 + 49 - 2 - 92 + 85 - 1 + 2)^7 \\
 &:= (13 + 49 + 2 + 9 - 28 - 5 - 12)^7 \\
 &:= (13 - 49 + 2 - 9 - 2 + 85 - 12)^7 \\
 &:= (13 - 49 - 2 - 9 + 2 + 85 - 12)^7 \\
 &:= (-13 - 4 + 92 - 92 - 8 + 51 + 2)^7 \\
 &:= (-13 - 4 - 92 + 92 - 8 + 51 + 2)^7 \\
 &:= (-13 - 4 - 9 + 29 - 28 + 51 + 2)^7 \\
 &:= (-13 + 4 - 9 - 29 + 2 + 85 - 12)^7 \\
 &:= (1 - 34 + 92 - 92 + 8 + 51 + 2)^7 \\
 &:= (1 - 34 - 92 + 92 + 8 + 51 + 2)^7 \\
 &:= (-1 + 34 - 9 + 29 + 28 - 51 - 2)^7 \\
 &:= (-1 - 34 + 9 + 29 - 28 + 51 + 2)^7 \\
 &:= (1 - 34 + 9 - 29 + 28 + 51 + 2)^7 \\
 &:= (1 + 34 + 9 + 29 - 28 - 5 - 12)^7 \\
 &:= (1 - 34 - 9 - 29 + 2 + 85 + 12)^7 \\
 &:= (-1 - 3 + 49 + 2 - 92 + 85 - 12)^7 \\
 &:= (-13 + 49 - 29 - 28 + 51 - 2)^7 \\
 &:= (-13 + 49 - 29 + 28 + 5 - 12)^7 \\
 &:= (13 - 49 + 29 + 28 - 5 + 12)^7 \\
 &:= (1 - 349 + 292 + 85 + 1 - 2)^7 \\
 &:= (-1 - 349 + 292 + 85 - 1 + 2)^7
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\mathbf{13498272341} := (1 + 3 + 49 - 8 + 2 - 7 + 2341)^3$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 \mathbf{13521270961} &:= (1 + 352 - 1 - 2 + 7 - 09 - 6 - 1)^4 \\
 &:= (-1 + 352 + 1 - 2 + 7 - 09 - 6 - 1)^4 \\
 &:= (1 + 352 + 1 - 2 - 7 - 09 + 6 - 1)^4 \\
 &:= (-1 + 352 - 1 + 2 - 7 - 09 + 6 - 1)^4 \\
 &:= (-1 + 352 - 1 - 2 + 7 - 09 - 6 + 1)^4 \\
 &:= (1 + 352 - 1 - 2 - 7 - 09 + 6 + 1)^4 \\
 &:= (-1 + 352 + 1 - 2 - 7 - 09 + 6 + 1)^4 \\
 &:= (1 + 352 + 1 - 27 + 09 + 6 - 1)^4 \\
 &:= (1 + 352 - 1 - 27 + 09 + 6 + 1)^4 \\
 &:= (-1 + 352 + 1 - 27 + 09 + 6 + 1)^4 \\
 &:= (1 + 3 + 52 + 1 + 270 + 9 + 6 - 1)^4 \\
 &:= (1 + 3 + 52 - 1 + 270 + 9 + 6 + 1)^4 \\
 &:= (-1 + 3 + 52 + 1 + 270 + 9 + 6 + 1)^4 \\
 &:= (13 + 5 + 2 - 1 + 270 - 9 + 61)^4 \\
 &:= (1 + 35 + 21 + 270 + 9 + 6 - 1)^4 \\
 &:= (-1 + 35 + 21 + 270 + 9 + 6 + 1)^4 \\
 &:= (-1 + 3 + 5 + 212 + 70 - 9 + 61)^4 \\
 &:= (-1 + 3 - 5 - 21 + 270 + 96 - 1)^4
 \end{aligned}$$

$:= (-13 + 521 - 2 - 70 - 96 + 1)^4$	$:= (-1 + 3 + 8 - 4 + 1 + 2 + 8 - 7 - 2 - 01)^{12}$
$:= (1 - 352 - 12 + 709 - 6 + 1)^4$	$:= (-1 + 3 + 8 + 4 - 1 - 2 - 8 + 7 - 2 - 01)^{12}$
$:= (1 + 352 - 12 + 70 - 9 - 61)^4$	$:= (1 - 3 + 8 + 4 - 1 + 2 - 8 + 7 - 2 - 01)^{12}$
$:= (1 + 352 - 12 - 70 + 9 + 61)^4$	$:= (1 + 3 + 8 - 4 + 1 + 2 - 8 + 7 - 2 - 01)^{12}$
$:= (-1 - 35 + 212 + 70 + 96 - 1)^4$	$:= (-1 - 3 + 8 + 4 + 1 + 2 - 8 + 7 - 2 - 01)^{12}$
$:= (1 - 352 + 1 - 270 + 961)^4$	$:= (-1 + 3 - 8 + 4 - 1 - 2 + 8 + 7 - 2 - 01)^{12}$
$:= (-1 + 35 - 2 + 1270 - 961)^4$	$:= (1 - 3 - 8 + 4 - 1 + 2 + 8 + 7 - 2 - 01)^{12}$
13532315887 $:= (-13 + 5 - 3 + 2315 - 8 + 87)^3$	$:= (1 + 3 - 8 - 4 + 1 + 2 + 8 + 7 - 2 - 01)^{12}$
$:= (-1 + 35 + 3231 + 5 - 887)^3$	$:= (-1 - 3 - 8 + 4 + 1 + 2 + 8 + 7 - 2 - 01)^{12}$
13549359104 $:= (1354 + 935 + 91 + 04)^3$	$:= (1 + 3 + 8 - 4 - 1 - 2 + 8 - 7 + 2 - 01)^{12}$
$:= (1354 + 935 - 9 + 104)^3$	$:= (-1 - 3 + 8 + 4 - 1 - 2 + 8 - 7 + 2 - 01)^{12}$
13661168161 $:= (1 - 3 + 66 + 116816 + 1)^2$	$:= (-1 + 3 + 8 - 4 + 1 - 2 + 8 - 7 + 2 - 01)^{12}$
13669062471 $:= (1 + 3 + 6 + 6 - 90 - 6 + 2471)^3$	$:= (1 - 3 + 8 - 4 + 1 + 2 + 8 - 7 + 2 - 01)^{12}$
$:= (1 + 3 + 6 - 6 - 90 + 6 + 2471)^3$	$:= (1 - 3 + 8 + 4 - 1 - 2 - 8 + 7 + 2 - 01)^{12}$
$:= (1 + 3 - 6 + 6 - 90 + 6 + 2471)^3$	$:= (1 + 3 + 8 - 4 + 1 - 2 - 8 + 7 + 2 - 01)^{12}$
13680577296 $:= (13 + 6 + 8 + 05 + 7 + 7 + 296)^4$	$:= (-1 - 3 + 8 + 4 + 1 - 2 - 8 + 7 + 2 - 01)^{12}$
$:= (-1 + 36 - 8 + 05 + 7 + 7 + 296)^4$	$:= (-1 + 3 + 8 - 4 - 1 + 2 - 8 + 7 + 2 - 01)^{12}$
$:= (1 - 3 + 6 - 8 + 057 - 7 + 296)^4$	$:= (1 - 3 - 8 + 4 - 1 - 2 + 8 + 7 + 2 - 01)^{12}$
$:= (-1 - 3 - 6 - 8 + 057 + 7 + 296)^4$	$:= (1 + 3 - 8 - 4 + 1 - 2 + 8 + 7 + 2 - 01)^{12}$
$:= (-13 + 68 + 05 - 7 - 7 + 296)^4$	$:= (-1 - 3 - 8 + 4 + 1 - 2 + 8 + 7 + 2 - 01)^{12}$
$:= (1 + 368 - 057 + 7 + 29 - 6)^4$	$:= (-1 + 3 - 8 - 4 - 1 + 2 + 8 + 7 + 2 - 01)^{12}$
$:= (-1 - 368 - 05 - 7 + 729 - 6)^4$	$:= (1 - 3 + 8 + 4 - 1 - 2 + 8 - 7 - 2 + 01)^{12}$
$:= (136 + 80 + 57 + 72 - 9 + 6)^4$	$:= (1 + 3 + 8 - 4 + 1 - 2 + 8 - 7 - 2 + 01)^{12}$
$:= (136 - 8 - 05 - 77 + 296)^4$	$:= (-1 - 3 + 8 + 4 + 1 - 2 + 8 - 7 - 2 + 01)^{12}$
$:= (1 + 36 + 80 + 57 + 72 + 96)^4$	$:= (-1 + 3 + 8 - 4 - 1 + 2 + 8 - 7 - 2 + 01)^{12}$
$:= (-13 - 6 + 80 + 577 - 296)^4$	$:= (1 - 3 + 8 + 4 + 1 - 2 - 8 + 7 - 2 + 01)^{12}$
13737779875 $:= (1 + 3 + 737 + 779 + 875)^3$	$:= (1 + 3 + 8 - 4 - 1 + 2 - 8 + 7 - 2 + 01)^{12}$
13769379649 $:= (1 + 37693 + 79649)^2$	$:= (-1 - 3 + 8 + 4 - 1 + 2 - 8 + 7 - 2 + 01)^{12}$
13772224773 $:= (1 + 3 - 77 - 2 - 2 + 2477 - 3)^3$	$:= (-1 + 3 + 8 - 4 + 1 + 2 - 8 + 7 - 2 + 01)^{12}$
$:= (-1 - 3 - 77 + 2 + 2 + 2477 - 3)^3$	$:= (1 - 3 - 8 + 4 + 1 - 2 + 8 + 7 - 2 + 01)^{12}$
$:= (1 - 3 - 77 - 2 - 2 + 2477 + 3)^3$	$:= (1 + 3 - 8 - 4 - 1 + 2 + 8 + 7 - 2 + 01)^{12}$
$:= (1 + 3 - 7 - 72 - 2 + 2477 - 3)^3$	$:= (-1 - 3 - 8 + 4 - 1 + 2 + 8 + 7 - 2 + 01)^{12}$
$:= (1 - 3 - 7 - 72 - 2 + 2477 + 3)^3$	$:= (-1 + 3 - 8 - 4 + 1 + 2 + 8 + 7 - 2 + 01)^{12}$
$:= (137 + 7 + 2 + 2247 + 7 - 3)^3$	$:= (1 + 3 + 8 + 4 + 1 + 2 - 8 - 7 + 2 + 01)^{12}$
$:= (-1 + 3 + 77 - 2 + 2247 + 73)^3$	$:= (-1 + 3 + 8 - 4 - 1 - 2 + 8 - 7 + 2 + 01)^{12}$
$:= (1 - 3 + 77 + 2 + 2247 + 73)^3$	$:= (1 - 3 + 8 - 4 - 1 + 2 + 8 - 7 + 2 + 01)^{12}$
$:= (1 - 3 + 7 + 72 + 2247 + 73)^3$	$:= (-1 - 3 + 8 - 4 + 1 + 2 + 8 - 7 + 2 + 01)^{12}$
13841287201 $:= (1 - 3 + 8 + 4 + 1 - 2 + 8 - 7 - 2 - 01)^{12}$	$:= (1 + 3 - 8 + 4 + 1 + 2 + 8 - 7 + 2 + 01)^{12}$
$:= (1 + 3 + 8 - 4 - 1 + 2 + 8 - 7 - 2 - 01)^{12}$	$:= (1 + 3 + 8 - 4 - 1 - 2 - 8 + 7 + 2 + 01)^{12}$
$:= (-1 - 3 + 8 + 4 - 1 + 2 + 8 - 7 - 2 - 01)^{12}$	$:= (-1 - 3 + 8 + 4 - 1 - 2 - 8 + 7 + 2 + 01)^{12}$

$$\begin{aligned} &:= (-1+3+8-4+1-2-8+7+2+01)^{12} \\ &:= (1-3+8-4+1+2-8+7+2+01)^{12} \\ &:= (1+3-8-4-1-2+8+7+2+01)^{12} \\ &:= (-1-3-8+4-1-2+8+7+2+01)^{12} \\ &:= (-1+3-8-4+1-2+8+7+2+01)^{12} \\ &:= (1-3-8-4+1+2+8+7+2+01)^{12} \\ &:= (1+3+8+41-2+8-7-2-01)^6 \\ &:= (-1+3+8+41+2-8+7-2-01)^6 \\ &:= (-1+3-8+41+2+8+7-2-01)^6 \\ &:= (-1-3+8+41+2+8-7+2-01)^6 \\ &:= (-1+3+8+41-2-8+7+2-01)^6 \\ &:= (1-3+8+41+2-8+7+2-01)^6 \\ &:= (-1+3-8+41-2+8+7+2-01)^6 \\ &:= (1-3-8+41+2+8+7+2-01)^6 \\ &:= (-1+3+8+41-2+8-7-2+01)^6 \\ &:= (1-3+8+41+2+8-7-2+01)^6 \\ &:= (1+3+8+41-2-8+7-2+01)^6 \\ &:= (1+3-8+41-2+8+7-2+01)^6 \\ &:= (1-3+8+41-2+8-7+2+01)^6 \\ &:= (-1-3+8+41+2-8+7+2+01)^6 \\ &:= (-1-3-8+41+2+8+7+2+01)^6 \\ &:= (-1+3-8-4-1+28-7-2-01)^{12} \\ &:= (1+3+8+4+1+28+7-2-01)^6 \\ &:= (1-3-8-4-1+28-7+2-01)^{12} \\ &:= (-1-3-8-4+1+28-7+2-01)^{12} \\ &:= (-1+3+8+4-1+28+7+2-01)^6 \\ &:= (1-3-8-4+1+28-7-2+01)^{12} \\ &:= (1+3+8+4-1+28+7-2+01)^6 \\ &:= (-1+3+8+4+1+28+7-2+01)^6 \\ &:= (-1-3-8-4-1+28-7+2+01)^{12} \\ &:= (1-3+8+4+1+28+7+2+01)^6 \\ &:= (1+3+8+4-1-2+8+7-20-1)^{12} \\ &:= (-1+3+8+4+1-2+8+7-20-1)^{12} \\ &:= (1-3+8+4+1+2+8+7-20-1)^{12} \\ &:= (-1+3+8-4-1-2-8-7+20-1)^{12} \\ &:= (1-3+8-4-1+2-8-7+20-1)^{12} \\ &:= (-1-3+8-4+1+2-8-7+20-1)^{12} \\ &:= (1+3-8+4+1+2-8-7+20-1)^{12} \\ &:= (-1+3-8-4-1-2+8-7+20-1)^{12} \\ &:= (1-3-8-4-1+2+8-7+20-1)^{12} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} &:= (-1-3-8-4+1+2+8-7+20-1)^{12} \\ &:= (1+3-8-4-1-2-8+7+20-1)^{12} \\ &:= (-1-3-8+4-1-2-8+7+20-1)^{12} \\ &:= (-1+3-8-4+1-2-8+7+20-1)^{12} \\ &:= (1-3-8-4+1+2-8+7+20-1)^{12} \\ &:= (1+3+8+4+1-2+8+7+20-1)^6 \\ &:= (-1+3+8+4-1+2+8+7+20-1)^6 \\ &:= (-1+3+8+4-1-2+8+7-20+1)^{12} \\ &:= (1-3+8+4-1+2+8+7-20+1)^{12} \\ &:= (1+3+8-4+1+2+8+7-20+1)^{12} \\ &:= (-1-3+8+4+1+2+8+7-20+1)^{12} \\ &:= (1-3+8-4+1-2-8-7+20+1)^{12} \\ &:= (-1-3+8-4-1+2-8-7+20+1)^{12} \\ &:= (1+3-8+4-1+2-8-7+20+1)^{12} \\ &:= (-1+3-8+4+1+2-8-7+20+1)^{12} \\ &:= (1-3-8-4+1-2+8-7+20+1)^{12} \\ &:= (-1-3-8-4-1+2-8-7+20+1)^{12} \\ &:= (1+3-8+4-1+2-8-7+20+1)^{12} \\ &:= (-1+3-8+4+1+2-8-7+20+1)^{12} \\ &:= (1-3-8-4+1-2+8-7+20+1)^{12} \\ &:= (-1-3-8-4-1+2+8-7+20+1)^{12} \\ &:= (-1+3-8-4-1-2-8+7+20+1)^{12} \\ &:= (1-3-8-4-1+2-8+7+20+1)^{12} \\ &:= (-1-3-8-4+1+2-8+7+20+1)^{12} \\ &:= (1+3+8+4-1-2+8+7+20+1)^6 \\ &:= (-1+3+8+4+1-2+8+7+20+1)^6 \\ &:= (1-3+8+4+1+2+8+7+20+1)^6 \\ &:= (-13+8+4+12-8+7-2-01)^{12} \\ &:= (-13-8+4+12+8+7-2-01)^{12} \\ &:= (13+8+4+12+8+7-2-01)^6 \\ &:= (13-8+4+12-8-7+2-01)^{12} \\ &:= (13+8-4-12+8-7+2-01)^{12} \\ &:= (-13+8-4+12+8-7+2+01)^{12} \\ &:= (13+8-4-12-8+7+2+01)^{12} \\ &:= (13-8-4-12+8+7+2+01)^{12} \\ &:= (-13-8+4+1+2-8+72-01)^6 \\ &:= (-13-8+4-1+2-8+72+01)^6 \\ &:= (-1+38+4+12-8+7-2-01)^6 \\ &:= (-1+38-4-12-8-7+2-01)^{12} \\ &:= (1+38-4+12+8-7+2-01)^6 \\ &:= (1+38-4-12-8-7-2+01)^{12} \\ &:= (-1+38-4+12+8-7+2+01)^6 \\ &:= (1+38-4+12-8+7+2+01)^6 \\ &:= (1+38+4-12+8+7+2+01)^6 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} &:= (1 - 38 + 4 + 1 + 2 + 8 + 72 - 01)^6 & &:= (-1 - 3 - 8 + 41 + 2 - 8 + 7 + 20 - 1)^6 \\ &:= (1 - 38 + 4 - 1 + 2 + 8 + 72 + 01)^6 & &:= (1 + 3 + 8 - 41 + 2 + 8 + 7 + 20 - 1)^{12} \\ &:= (-1 - 38 + 4 + 1 + 2 + 8 + 72 + 01)^6 & &:= (-1 - 3 - 8 + 41 - 2 - 8 + 7 - 20 + 1)^{12} \\ &:= (1 + 3 + 84 - 1 - 28 - 7 - 2 - 01)^6 & &:= (-1 + 3 + 8 + 41 + 2 + 8 + 7 - 20 + 1)^6 \\ &:= (-1 + 3 + 84 + 1 - 28 - 7 - 2 - 01)^6 & &:= (-1 - 3 + 8 + 41 - 2 - 8 - 7 + 20 + 1)^6 \\ &:= (1 - 3 + 84 + 1 - 28 - 7 + 2 - 01)^6 & &:= (-1 - 3 - 8 + 41 - 2 + 8 - 7 + 20 + 1)^6 \\ &:= (-1 + 3 + 84 - 1 - 28 - 7 - 2 + 01)^6 & &:= (1 - 3 - 8 + 41 - 2 - 8 + 7 + 20 + 1)^6 \\ &:= (1 - 3 + 84 - 1 - 28 - 7 + 2 + 01)^6 & &:= (-1 + 3 + 8 - 41 + 2 + 8 + 7 + 20 + 1)^{12} \\ &:= (-1 - 3 + 84 + 1 - 28 - 7 + 2 + 01)^6 & &:= (-1 + 3 - 8 + 4 - 12 - 8 + 72 - 01)^6 \\ &:= (1 + 3 - 84 + 1 + 2 + 87 - 2 - 01)^{12} & &:= (1 + 3 + 8 - 4 - 1 + 28 - 7 - 20 - 1)^{12} \\ &:= (1 + 3 - 84 + 1 - 2 + 87 + 2 - 01)^{12} & &:= (-1 - 3 + 8 + 4 - 1 + 28 - 7 - 20 - 1)^{12} \\ &:= (-1 + 3 - 84 - 1 + 2 + 87 + 2 - 01)^{12} & &:= (-1 + 3 + 8 - 4 + 1 + 28 - 7 - 20 - 1)^{12} \\ &:= (1 + 3 - 84 - 1 + 2 + 87 - 2 + 01)^{12} & &:= (1 - 3 - 8 + 4 - 1 + 28 + 7 - 20 - 1)^{12} \\ &:= (-1 + 3 - 84 + 1 + 2 + 87 - 2 + 01)^{12} & &:= (1 + 3 - 8 - 4 + 1 + 28 + 7 - 20 - 1)^{12} \\ &:= (1 + 3 + 84 + 1 + 2 - 87 + 2 + 01)^{12} & &:= (-1 - 3 - 8 + 4 + 1 + 28 + 7 - 20 - 1)^{12} \\ &:= (1 + 3 - 84 - 1 - 2 + 87 + 2 + 01)^{12} & &:= (1 - 3 + 8 + 4 - 1 + 28 - 7 + 20 - 1)^6 \\ &:= (-1 + 3 - 84 + 1 - 2 + 87 + 2 + 01)^{12} & &:= (1 + 3 + 8 - 4 + 1 + 28 - 7 + 20 - 1)^6 \\ &:= (1 - 3 - 84 + 1 + 2 + 87 + 2 + 01)^{12} & &:= (-1 - 3 + 8 + 4 + 1 + 28 - 7 + 20 - 1)^6 \\ &:= (1 + 3 + 84 - 1 - 2 - 8 - 7 - 20 - 1)^6 & &:= (1 - 3 + 8 + 4 - 1 - 28 + 7 + 20 - 1)^{12} \\ &:= (-1 + 3 + 84 + 1 - 2 - 8 - 7 - 20 - 1)^6 & &:= (1 + 3 + 8 - 4 + 1 - 28 + 7 + 20 - 1)^{12} \\ &:= (1 - 3 + 84 + 1 + 2 - 8 - 7 - 20 - 1)^6 & &:= (-1 - 3 + 8 + 4 + 1 - 28 + 7 + 20 - 1)^{12} \\ &:= (-1 + 3 + 84 - 1 - 2 - 8 - 7 - 20 + 1)^6 & &:= (1 - 3 - 8 + 4 + 1 + 28 + 7 + 20 - 1)^6 \\ &:= (1 - 3 + 84 - 1 + 2 - 8 - 7 - 20 + 1)^6 & &:= (-1 + 3 + 8 - 4 - 1 + 28 - 7 - 20 + 1)^{12} \\ &:= (-1 - 3 + 84 + 1 + 2 - 8 - 7 - 20 + 1)^6 & &:= (1 + 3 - 8 - 4 - 1 + 28 + 7 - 20 + 1)^{12} \\ &:= (-1 - 3 + 8 + 41 - 28 - 7 - 2 - 01)^{12} & &:= (-1 - 3 - 8 + 4 - 1 + 28 + 7 - 20 + 1)^{12} \\ &:= (1 - 3 - 8 + 41 + 28 - 7 - 2 - 01)^6 & &:= (-1 + 3 - 8 - 4 + 1 + 28 + 7 - 20 + 1)^{12} \\ &:= (1 - 3 - 8 + 41 - 28 + 7 - 2 - 01)^{12} & &:= (1 + 3 + 8 - 4 - 1 + 28 - 7 + 20 + 1)^6 \\ &:= (1 + 3 + 8 - 41 + 28 + 7 + 2 - 01)^{12} & &:= (-1 - 3 + 8 + 4 - 1 + 28 - 7 + 20 + 1)^6 \\ &:= (-1 - 3 - 8 + 41 + 28 - 7 - 2 + 01)^6 & &:= (-1 + 3 + 8 - 4 + 1 + 28 - 7 + 20 + 1)^6 \\ &:= (-1 - 3 - 8 + 41 - 28 + 7 - 2 + 01)^{12} & &:= (1 + 3 + 8 - 4 - 1 - 28 + 7 + 20 + 1)^{12} \\ &:= (-1 + 3 + 8 - 41 + 28 + 7 + 2 + 01)^{12} & &:= (-1 - 3 + 8 + 4 - 1 - 28 + 7 + 20 + 1)^{12} \\ &:= (-1 - 3 + 8 - 41 + 2 + 87 - 2 - 01)^6 & &:= (-1 + 3 + 8 - 4 + 1 - 28 + 7 + 20 + 1)^{12} \\ &:= (-1 - 3 + 8 - 41 - 2 + 87 + 2 - 01)^6 & &:= (1 - 3 - 8 + 4 - 1 + 28 + 7 + 20 + 1)^6 \\ &:= (1 - 3 + 8 - 41 - 2 + 87 - 2 + 01)^6 & &:= (1 + 3 - 8 - 4 + 1 + 28 + 7 + 20 + 1)^6 \\ &:= (-1 - 3 + 8 + 41 - 2 - 8 - 7 - 20 - 1)^{12} & &:= (-1 - 3 - 8 + 4 + 1 + 28 + 7 + 20 + 1)^6 \\ &:= (-1 - 3 - 8 + 41 - 2 + 8 - 7 - 20 - 1)^{12} & &:= (1 - 3 - 8 - 4 - 1 - 2 + 87 - 20 - 1)^6 \\ &:= (1 - 3 - 8 + 41 - 2 - 8 + 7 - 20 - 1)^{12} & &:= (-1 - 3 - 8 - 4 + 1 - 2 + 87 - 20 - 1)^6 \\ &:= (1 + 3 + 8 + 41 + 2 + 8 + 7 - 20 - 1)^6 & &:= (-1 - 3 - 8 - 4 - 1 - 2 + 87 - 20 + 1)^6 \\ &:= (1 - 3 + 8 + 41 - 2 - 8 - 7 + 20 - 1)^6 & &:= (138 + 4 - 1 - 2 - 87 - 2 - 01)^6 \\ &:= (1 - 3 - 8 + 41 - 2 + 8 - 7 + 20 - 1)^6 & &:= (138 - 4 - 1 + 2 - 87 + 2 - 01)^6 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} & := (138 - 4 + 1 + 2 - 87 - 2 + 01)^6 & := (-1 + 3 + 8 + 41 - 28 + 7 + 20 - 1)^6 \\ & := (138 - 4 + 1 - 2 - 87 + 2 + 01)^6 & := (-1 + 3 - 8 - 41 + 28 + 7 + 20 - 1)^{12} \\ & := (-13 + 84 - 1 + 2 + 8 - 72 - 01)^{12} & := (1 - 3 + 8 + 41 + 28 - 7 - 20 + 1)^6 \\ & := (13 - 84 + 1 - 2 + 8 + 72 - 01)^{12} & := (1 - 3 + 8 + 41 - 28 + 7 - 20 + 1)^{12} \\ & := (-13 + 84 + 1 - 2 + 8 - 72 + 01)^{12} & := (1 - 3 + 8 - 41 + 28 - 7 + 20 + 1)^{12} \\ & := (13 - 84 - 1 - 2 + 8 + 72 + 01)^{12} & := (1 - 3 - 8 + 4 + 128 - 72 - 01)^6 \\ & := (-13 - 8 - 4 - 12 + 87 - 2 + 01)^6 & := (1 + 3 - 8 - 4 + 128 - 72 + 01)^6 \\ & := (13 + 8 - 4 + 12 - 8 + 7 - 20 - 1)^{12} & := (-1 - 3 - 8 + 4 + 128 - 72 + 01)^6 \\ & := (13 + 8 + 4 - 12 + 8 + 7 - 20 - 1)^{12} & := (138 - 41 - 2 - 87 - 2 + 01)^{12} \\ & := (13 - 8 - 4 + 12 + 8 + 7 - 20 - 1)^{12} & := (138 + 4 - 12 - 8 - 72 - 01)^6 \\ & := (-13 + 8 - 4 + 12 - 8 - 7 + 20 - 1)^{12} & := (-138 + 4 - 1 - 2 - 8 - 7 + 201)^6 \\ & := (-13 + 8 + 4 - 12 + 8 - 7 + 20 - 1)^{12} & := (138 + 4 + 1 - 2 + 8 - 7 + 201)^4 \\ & := (-13 - 8 - 4 + 12 + 8 - 7 + 20 - 1)^{12} & := (138 + 4 - 1 + 2 - 8 + 7 + 201)^4 \\ & := (13 + 8 - 4 + 12 + 8 - 7 + 20 - 1)^6 & := (13 - 84 + 128 - 7 - 2 + 01)^6 \\ & := (13 - 8 - 4 - 12 - 8 + 7 + 20 - 1)^{12} & := (13 - 84 - 12 + 87 + 2 + 01)^{12} \\ & := (-13 + 8 + 4 + 12 + 8 + 7 - 20 + 1)^{12} & := (13 + 84 - 12 - 8 - 7 - 20 - 1)^6 \\ & := (-13 + 8 + 4 - 12 - 8 + 7 + 20 + 1)^{12} & := (-13 + 84 + 12 - 8 - 7 - 20 + 1)^6 \\ & := (-13 - 8 - 4 + 12 - 8 + 7 + 20 + 1)^{12} & := (13 + 8 + 412 - 87 - 2 - 01)^4 \\ & := (13 + 8 - 4 + 12 - 8 + 7 + 20 + 1)^6 & := (13 - 8 - 41 - 28 + 72 - 01)^{12} \\ & := (-13 - 8 + 4 - 12 + 8 + 7 + 20 + 1)^{12} & := (1 + 384 + 1 + 28 - 72 + 01)^4 \\ & := (13 + 8 + 4 - 12 + 8 + 7 + 20 + 1)^6 & := (1 - 384 + 1 - 2 + 8 + 720 - 1)^4 \\ & := (13 - 8 - 4 + 12 + 8 + 7 + 20 + 1)^6 & := (-1 - 384 - 1 + 2 + 8 + 720 - 1)^4 \\ & := (-1 + 38 + 4 - 12 - 8 + 7 - 20 - 1)^{12} & := (1 - 384 - 1 - 2 + 8 + 720 + 1)^4 \\ & := (1 + 38 + 4 + 12 + 8 + 7 - 20 - 1)^6 & := (-1 - 384 + 1 - 2 + 8 + 720 + 1)^4 \\ & := (-1 + 38 - 4 + 12 - 8 - 7 + 20 - 1)^6 & := (1 - 38 + 41 - 28 + 72 + 01)^6 \\ & := (-1 + 38 + 4 - 12 + 8 - 7 + 20 - 1)^6 & := (1 + 3 - 8 + 41 + 287 + 20 - 1)^4 \\ & := (1 + 38 + 4 - 12 - 8 + 7 + 20 - 1)^6 & := (-1 + 3 - 8 + 41 + 287 + 20 + 1)^4 \\ & := (-1 + 38 + 4 + 12 + 8 + 7 - 20 + 1)^6 & := (1 + 3 + 8 + 41 + 2 + 87 + 201)^4 \\ & := (-1 + 38 + 4 - 12 - 8 + 7 + 20 + 1)^6 & := (-138 + 41 - 2 + 87 + 20 - 1)^{12} \\ & := (1 - 38 - 4 + 12 + 8 + 7 + 20 + 1)^{12} & := (138 + 4 + 128 + 72 + 01)^4 \\ & := (-1 - 38 + 4 - 1 - 28 + 72 - 01)^{12} & := (13 - 84 + 12 + 87 - 20 - 1)^{12} \\ & := (1 - 3 + 84 - 12 + 8 - 72 + 01)^{12} & := (13 - 84 + 12 + 87 + 20 + 1)^6 \\ & := (1 - 3 - 84 + 12 + 8 + 72 + 01)^{12} & := (-13 - 8 + 4 - 128 - 7 + 201)^6 \\ & := (1 + 3 + 84 + 1 - 28 + 7 - 20 + 1)^6 & := (1 + 38 + 412 - 87 - 20 - 1)^4 \\ & := (1 + 3 + 8 + 412 - 8 - 72 - 01)^4 & := (-1 + 38 + 412 - 87 - 20 + 1)^4 \\ & := (1 + 3 - 8 + 412 + 8 - 72 - 01)^4 & := (1 + 38 + 4 + 12 + 87 + 201)^4 \\ & := (-1 + 3 + 8 + 412 - 8 - 72 + 01)^4 & := (1 + 3 - 84 + 1 + 287 - 201)^{12} \\ & := (-1 + 3 - 8 + 412 + 8 - 72 + 01)^4 & := (-1 - 3 + 8 - 41 + 287 - 201)^6 \\ & := (1 + 3 + 8 + 41 + 287 + 2 + 01)^4 & := (138 - 4 + 1 - 287 + 201)^6 \\ & := (-1 + 3 - 8 + 41 + 28 + 7 - 20 - 1)^6 & := (1 + 384 - 128 - 7 - 201)^6 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 13893235264 &:= (-1 + 3 - 8 - 9 + 3 + 2352 + 64)^3 \\ &:= (-1 - 38 + 93 + 2352 - 6 + 4)^3 \end{aligned}$$

$$13927939416 := (-1 + 39 + 2793 - 9 - 416)^3$$

$$13962701312 := (1 + 3 + 9 + 6 + 2701 - 312)^3$$

$$13967221489 := (139672 - 21489)^2$$

$$\begin{aligned} 14003408896 &:= (-1 + 4 + 00340 + 8 + 8 - 9 - 6)^4 \\ &:= (1 + 4 + 00340 - 8 - 8 + 9 + 6)^4 \\ &:= (1 + 400 + 34 - 088 - 9 + 6)^4 \\ &:= (1 + 400 + 34 - 08 - 89 + 6)^4 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 14014952531 &:= (1401 + 4 + 952 + 53 + 1)^3 \\ &:= (1 - 40 + 14 - 95 + 2531)^3 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 14025517307 &:= (14 + 02 + 5 + 5 + 1 + 73 + 07)^5 \\ &:= (1 + 4 + 02 + 55 + 1 + 7 + 30 + 7)^5 \\ &:= (1 - 4 - 02 - 5 + 51 + 73 - 07)^5 \\ &:= (1 + 4 + 02 + 5 + 51 + 7 + 30 + 7)^5 \\ &:= (140 + 2 + 5 - 51 + 7 - 3 + 07)^5 \\ &:= (140 - 2 - 5 - 5 - 17 + 3 - 07)^5 \\ &:= (140 + 2 + 5 + 5 - 1 - 7 - 30 - 7)^5 \\ &:= (140 - 2 + 5 - 5 - 1 + 7 - 30 - 7)^5 \\ &:= (140 - 2 - 5 + 5 - 1 + 7 - 30 - 7)^5 \\ &:= (140 - 2 + 5 - 5 - 1 - 7 - 30 + 7)^5 \\ &:= (140 - 2 - 5 + 5 - 1 - 7 - 30 + 7)^5 \\ &:= (14 + 025 + 51 + 7 + 3 + 07)^5 \\ &:= (1 + 40 - 2 + 55 + 17 + 3 - 07)^5 \\ &:= (-1 + 40 - 2 + 55 - 1 - 7 + 30 - 7)^5 \\ &:= (1 + 40 + 2 + 5 + 5 + 17 + 30 + 7)^5 \\ &:= (140 - 25 + 5 - 17 - 3 + 07)^5 \\ &:= (14 - 02 + 55 + 17 + 30 - 7)^5 \\ &:= (1 - 402 - 5 + 517 + 3 - 07)^5 \\ &:= (1 - 40 - 25 + 5 + 173 - 07)^5 \\ &:= (140 + 2 - 55 - 17 + 30 + 7)^5 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 14049858997 &:= (1404 - 9 + 8 + 5 + 8 + 997)^3 \\ &:= (1404 + 98 + 5 + 899 + 7)^3 \end{aligned}$$

$$14084823375 := (1 - 4 + 084 - 8 + 2337 + 5)^3$$

$$14088977809 := (-1 + 40889 + 77809)^2$$

$$14102327296 := (1 + 4 - 10 + 2327 - 2 + 96)^3$$

$$14119845713 := (-141 + 1984 + 571 + 3)^3$$

$$\begin{aligned} 14154926059 &:= (-141 - 5 - 49 + 2605 + 9)^3 \\ &:= (-14 - 154 - 9 + 2605 - 9)^3 \end{aligned}$$

$$14166950625 := (-1 + 416 + 6 - 95 - 06 + 25)^4$$

$$\begin{aligned} &:= (-1 + 416 - 6 - 95 + 06 + 25)^4 \\ &:= (1 + 416 + 6 - 9 - 50 + 6 - 25)^4 \end{aligned}$$

$$:= (-1 + 4 - 166 + 9 + 506 - 2 - 5)^4$$

$$:= (-1 - 416 + 695 + 062 + 5)^4$$

$$:= (-1 + 416 - 695 + 0625)^4$$

$$\begin{aligned} 14242881024 &:= (-1 - 4 + 2428 + 8 - 1 - 02 - 4)^3 \\ &:= (1 + 4 + 2428 - 8 + 1 + 02 - 4)^3 \\ &:= (-1 + 4 + 2428 - 8 - 1 - 02 + 4)^3 \\ &:= (1 - 4 + 2428 - 8 + 1 + 02 + 4)^3 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 14331199589 &:= (1433 + 1 + 1 + 995 + 8 - 9)^3 \\ &:= (1433 + 1 - 1 + 995 - 8 + 9)^3 \end{aligned}$$

$$:= (1433 - 1 + 1 + 995 - 8 + 9)^3$$

$$:= (1 + 433 + 1 + 1995 + 8 - 9)^3$$

$$:= (1 + 433 - 1 + 1995 - 8 + 9)^3$$

$$:= (-1 + 433 + 1 + 1995 - 8 + 9)^3$$

$$:= (14 + 331 + 1995 + 89)^3$$

$$14331920656 := (-1 + 4 + 331 + 9 - 2 + 06 + 5 - 6)^4$$

$$:= (1 - 4 + 331 + 9 + 2 + 06 - 5 + 6)^4$$

$$:= (-1 + 4 + 331 + 9 - 2 - 06 + 5 + 6)^4$$

$$:= (1 + 4 + 331 - 9 + 2 + 06 + 5 + 6)^4$$

$$:= (1 + 4 + 3 + 319 + 2 + 06 + 5 + 6)^4$$

$$:= (1 + 433 - 1 - 92 + 06 + 5 - 6)^4$$

$$:= (-1 + 433 + 1 - 92 + 06 + 5 - 6)^4$$

$$:= (-1 + 433 - 1 - 92 + 06 - 5 + 6)^4$$

$$:= (1 + 433 - 1 - 92 - 06 + 5 + 6)^4$$

$$:= (-1 + 433 + 1 - 92 - 06 + 5 + 6)^4$$

$$:= (-1 + 43 + 319 + 2 - 06 - 5 - 6)^4$$

$$:= (-1 + 4 + 331 + 9 + 20 - 6 - 5 - 6)^4$$

$$:= (1 - 4 + 331 - 9 + 20 + 6 - 5 + 6)^4$$

$$:= (1 + 4 - 3 + 319 + 20 + 6 + 5 - 6)^4$$

$$:= (-1 + 4 - 3 + 319 + 20 + 6 - 5 + 6)^4$$

$$:= (1 - 4 + 3 + 319 + 20 + 6 - 5 + 6)^4$$

$$:= (1 + 4 - 3 + 319 + 20 - 6 + 5 + 6)^4$$

$$:= (1 + 433 - 19 + 2 - 065 - 6)^4$$

$$:= (-1 + 43 + 319 - 20 + 6 + 5 - 6)^4$$

$$:= (-1 + 43 + 319 - 20 - 6 + 5 + 6)^4$$

$$:= (1 - 43 + 319 - 2 + 065 + 6)^4$$

$$:= (14 - 331 + 9 - 2 + 0656)^4$$

$$:= (14 - 3 - 319 - 2 + 0656)^4$$

$$:= (1 + 43 + 31 + 9 + 206 + 56)^4$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 & := (-14 + 3 - 319 + 20 + 656)^4 \\
 \mathbf{14419882504} & := (14 - 4 - 1 + 9 - 88 + 2504)^3 \\
 & := (-1 - 4 + 41 - 98 - 8 + 2504)^3 \\
 & := (-1 + 4 - 4 + 19 - 88 + 2504)^3 \\
 & := (-1 - 4 + 4 + 19 - 88 + 2504)^3 \\
 & := (-14 + 41 - 9 - 88 + 2504)^3 \\
 \mathbf{14437662875} & := (1 - 4 - 437 + 6 - 6 + 2875)^3 \\
 & := (1 - 4 - 437 - 6 + 6 + 2875)^3 \\
 \mathbf{14491091672} & := (1449 + 1 + 0916 + 72)^3 \\
 \mathbf{14498327281} & := (14 - 4 + 9 + 8 + 327 + 2 - 8 - 1)^4 \\
 & := (14 - 4 + 9 - 8 + 327 + 2 + 8 - 1)^4 \\
 & := (14 - 4 - 9 + 8 + 327 + 2 + 8 + 1)^4 \\
 & := (1 + 449 - 83 - 2 - 7 - 2 - 8 - 1)^4 \\
 & := (-1 + 449 - 83 - 2 - 7 - 2 - 8 + 1)^4 \\
 & := (1 + 449 - 8 - 3 - 2 - 7 - 2 - 81)^4 \\
 & := (-1 + 44 + 9 + 8 - 3 + 2 + 7 + 281)^4 \\
 & := (-1 + 4 + 49 + 8 - 3 + 2 + 7 + 281)^4 \\
 & := (1 - 4 + 49 + 8 + 3 + 2 + 7 + 281)^4 \\
 & := (1 + 4 - 4 - 9 + 83 - 2 - 7 + 281)^4 \\
 & := (1 - 4 + 4 - 9 + 83 - 2 - 7 + 281)^4 \\
 & := (-14 + 49 - 8 + 327 + 2 - 8 - 1)^4 \\
 & := (14 + 49 + 8 - 3 + 272 + 8 - 1)^4 \\
 & := (14 - 4 - 9 + 83 + 272 - 8 - 1)^4 \\
 & := (-14 + 4 + 9 + 83 + 272 - 8 + 1)^4 \\
 & := (14 - 4 - 9 - 8 + 327 + 28 - 1)^4 \\
 & := (-14 + 4 + 9 - 8 + 327 + 28 + 1)^4 \\
 & := (14 - 4 + 9 + 8 + 32 + 7 + 281)^4 \\
 & := (-14 + 4 + 9 - 8 + 3 + 272 + 81)^4 \\
 & := (-1 + 449 - 83 - 27 + 2 + 8 - 1)^4 \\
 & := (1 + 449 - 83 - 27 - 2 + 8 + 1)^4 \\
 & := (1 + 449 - 83 + 2 + 7 - 28 - 1)^4 \\
 & := (-1 + 449 - 83 + 2 + 7 - 28 + 1)^4 \\
 & := (1 + 449 + 8 - 32 - 72 - 8 + 1)^4 \\
 & := (1 + 449 - 8 - 32 - 72 + 8 + 1)^4 \\
 & := (-1 + 449 + 8 - 3 - 27 + 2 - 81)^4 \\
 & := (-1 + 44 - 9 + 8 - 3 + 27 + 281)^4 \\
 & := (-1 + 4 + 498 - 3 + 2 - 72 - 81)^4 \\
 & := (1 - 4 + 498 + 3 + 2 - 72 - 81)^4 \\
 & := (-1 - 4 + 49 - 8 + 3 + 27 + 281)^4 \\
 & := (1 + 4 - 4 + 98 + 327 + 2 - 81)^4
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 & := (1 - 4 + 4 + 98 + 327 + 2 - 81)^4 \\
 & := (-1 + 4 + 4 + 98 - 32 - 7 + 281)^4 \\
 & := (1 - 4 - 4 + 98 - 32 + 7 + 281)^4 \\
 & := (1 + 4 - 4 + 9 + 83 - 27 + 281)^4 \\
 & := (1 - 4 + 4 + 9 + 83 - 27 + 281)^4 \\
 & := (-14 + 49 - 8 + 32 + 7 + 281)^4 \\
 & := (1 + 4 - 49 + 83 + 27 + 281)^4 \\
 & := (1 + 449 - 832 + 728 + 1)^4 \\
 \mathbf{14562534888} & := (1 + 4 + 5 - 6 + 2534 - 88 - 8)^3 \\
 & := (-1 + 4 - 5 + 6 + 2534 - 88 - 8)^3 \\
 & := (1 + 4 + 5 - 6 + 2534 - 8 - 88)^3 \\
 & := (-1 + 4 - 5 + 6 + 2534 - 8 - 88)^3 \\
 \mathbf{14580432307} & := (145 - 8 - 04 + 3 + 2307)^3 \\
 & := (1 + 4 + 5 - 804 + 3230 + 7)^3 \\
 \mathbf{14634212536} & := (14 - 63 - 42 + 1 + 2536)^3 \\
 \mathbf{14666178816} & := (146 + 6 - 6 + 178 + 8 + 16)^4 \\
 & := (146 - 6 + 6 + 178 + 8 + 16)^4 \\
 & := (1 - 466 + 6 - 17 + 8 + 816)^4 \\
 \mathbf{14688124849} & := (1 - 4 - 6 - 8 - 8 - 1 + 2484 - 9)^3 \\
 & := (-1 - 4 - 6 - 8 - 8 + 1 + 2484 - 9)^3 \\
 & := (1 - 46 + 8 - 8 + 1 + 2484 + 9)^3 \\
 & := (1 - 46 - 8 + 8 + 1 + 2484 + 9)^3 \\
 & := (-1 + 46 - 88 - 1 + 2484 + 9)^3 \\
 & := (1 + 46 + 8 - 81 + 2484 - 9)^3 \\
 & := (-1 + 46 - 8 - 81 + 2484 + 9)^3 \\
 & := (1468 + 8 + 124 + 849)^3 \\
 \mathbf{14693280768} & := (1 + 4 + 69 + 3 + 2 + 8 + 07 + 6 + 8)^5 \\
 & := (-1 + 4 + 6 + 9 + 3 + 2 + 80 + 7 + 6 - 8)^5 \\
 & := (-1 + 4 + 6 + 9 + 3 - 2 + 80 + 7 - 6 + 8)^5 \\
 & := (1 + 4 + 6 + 9 - 3 + 2 + 80 + 7 - 6 + 8)^5 \\
 & := (1 + 4 + 6 + 9 + 3 - 2 + 80 - 7 + 6 + 8)^5 \\
 & := (1 - 4 + 6 + 9 - 3 - 2 + 80 + 7 + 6 + 8)^5 \\
 & := (-1 + 4 - 6 + 9 + 3 - 2 + 80 + 7 + 6 + 8)^5 \\
 & := (1 + 4 - 6 + 9 - 3 + 2 + 80 + 7 + 6 + 8)^5 \\
 & := (1 + 4 + 6 - 9 + 3 + 2 + 80 + 7 + 6 + 8)^5 \\
 & := (1 + 4 + 6 + 9 + 3 + 2 + 8 + 07 + 68)^5 \\
 & := (14 + 6 + 93 - 2 - 8 + 07 + 6 - 8)^5 \\
 & := (14 - 6 + 9 - 3 + 2 + 8 + 076 + 8)^5 \\
 & := (14 + 6 - 9 + 3 + 2 + 8 + 076 + 8)^5 \\
 & := (1 + 46 + 9 + 3 + 28 + 07 + 6 + 8)^5
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 &:= (-1 + 46 + 9 - 3 - 2 + 80 - 7 - 6 - 8)^5 \\
 &:= (-1 + 46 - 9 - 3 + 2 + 80 + 7 - 6 - 8)^5 \\
 &:= (-1 + 46 - 9 + 3 - 2 + 80 - 7 + 6 - 8)^5 \\
 &:= (1 + 46 - 9 - 3 + 2 + 80 - 7 + 6 - 8)^5 \\
 &:= (1 + 46 - 9 - 3 - 2 + 80 - 7 - 6 + 8)^5 \\
 &:= (-1 + 46 + 9 + 3 - 2 - 8 - 07 + 68)^5 \\
 &:= (1 + 46 + 9 - 3 + 2 - 8 - 07 + 68)^5 \\
 &:= (1 + 46 - 9 + 3 - 2 + 8 - 07 + 68)^5 \\
 &:= (-1 + 46 - 9 + 3 + 2 - 8 + 07 + 68)^5 \\
 &:= (-1 + 4 + 69 + 3 + 28 + 07 + 6 - 8)^5 \\
 &:= (1 + 4 + 69 - 3 + 28 + 07 - 6 + 8)^5 \\
 &:= (-1 + 4 + 6 - 9 + 32 + 8 + 076 - 8)^5 \\
 &:= (1 - 4 - 6 + 9 + 32 + 8 + 076 - 8)^5 \\
 &:= (-1 + 4 + 6 - 9 + 32 - 8 + 076 + 8)^5 \\
 &:= (1 - 4 - 6 + 9 + 32 - 8 + 076 + 8)^5 \\
 &:= (1 + 4 - 6 + 9 - 3 + 28 + 07 + 68)^5 \\
 &:= (1 + 4 + 6 - 9 + 3 + 28 + 07 + 68)^5 \\
 &:= (146 + 9 - 32 - 8 + 07 - 6 - 8)^5 \\
 &:= (146 - 9 - 32 + 8 - 07 - 6 + 8)^5 \\
 &:= (14 - 6 + 93 + 28 - 07 - 6 - 8)^5 \\
 &:= (-14 + 6 + 93 + 28 - 07 - 6 + 8)^5 \\
 &:= (-14 - 6 + 93 + 28 - 07 + 6 + 8)^5 \\
 &:= (14 - 6 + 9 + 32 + 80 - 7 - 6 - 8)^5 \\
 &:= (-14 + 6 + 9 + 32 + 80 - 7 - 6 + 8)^5 \\
 &:= (-14 - 6 + 9 + 32 + 80 - 7 + 6 + 8)^5 \\
 &:= (14 - 6 - 9 - 3 + 28 + 076 + 8)^5 \\
 &:= (-1 - 46 + 93 + 2 - 8 + 076 - 8)^5 \\
 &:= (-1 - 46 + 9 + 3 + 2 + 80 - 7 + 68)^5 \\
 &:= (-1 - 4 + 69 - 32 + 8 + 076 - 8)^5 \\
 &:= (-1 - 4 + 69 - 32 - 8 + 076 + 8)^5 \\
 &:= (-1 + 4 + 69 + 3 - 28 - 07 + 68)^5 \\
 &:= (-1 - 4 + 69 - 3 - 28 + 07 + 68)^5 \\
 &:= (-1 - 4 + 6 + 93 + 2 + 80 - 76 + 8)^5 \\
 &:= (-1 + 4 + 6 + 93 + 2 - 80 + 76 + 8)^5 \\
 &:= (-1 - 4 + 6 - 9 - 32 + 80 + 76 - 8)^5 \\
 &:= (146 - 93 + 2 - 8 - 07 + 68)^5 \\
 &:= (-14 + 69 - 32 + 80 + 7 + 6 - 8)^5 \\
 &:= (-14 + 69 - 3 - 28 + 076 + 8)^5 \\
 &:= (14 - 69 - 3 + 2 + 80 + 76 + 8)^5 \\
 &:= (14 - 6 + 93 + 2 + 80 - 7 - 68)^5
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 &:= (14 - 6 - 9 - 32 + 80 - 7 + 68)^5 \\
 &:= (1 - 4 - 69 + 32 + 80 + 76 - 8)^5 \\
 &:= (-1 - 4 + 69 + 32 + 80 - 76 + 8)^5 \\
 &:= (-1 + 4 + 69 + 32 - 80 + 76 + 8)^5 \\
 &:= (-1 + 4 - 6 + 932 - 807 - 6 - 8)^5 \\
 &:= (-1 - 4 - 6 - 93 + 280 - 76 + 8)^5 \\
 &:= (1 + 4 - 693 + 28 + 0768)^5 \\
 &**14724139851** := (1 - 4 + 7 + 2413 - 9 - 8 + 51)^3 \\
 &:= (-1 - 4 - 7 + 2413 - 9 + 8 + 51)^3 \\
 &**14832537993** := (1 + 4 + 8 + 3 + 2537 - 99 + 3)^3 \\
 &:= (14 - 8 + 3253 - 799 - 3)^3 \\
 &**14835483601** := (1 + 4 + 8 + 354 - 8 - 3 - 6 - 01)^4 \\
 &:= (1 + 4 - 8 + 354 + 8 - 3 - 6 - 01)^4 \\
 &:= (-1 + 4 - 8 + 354 - 8 + 3 + 6 - 01)^4 \\
 &:= (-1 + 4 + 8 + 354 - 8 - 3 - 6 + 01)^4 \\
 &:= (-1 + 4 - 8 + 354 + 8 - 3 - 6 + 01)^4 \\
 &:= (1 - 4 + 8 + 354 - 8 + 3 - 6 + 01)^4 \\
 &:= (1 - 4 - 8 + 354 + 8 + 3 - 6 + 01)^4 \\
 &:= (-14 + 8 + 3 + 5 - 4 - 8 + 360 - 1)^4 \\
 &:= (-14 + 8 - 3 - 5 - 4 + 8 + 360 - 1)^4 \\
 &:= (-14 - 8 + 3 + 5 - 4 + 8 + 360 - 1)^4 \\
 &:= (-14 + 8 + 3 - 5 + 4 - 8 + 360 + 1)^4 \\
 &:= (-14 - 8 + 3 - 5 + 4 + 8 + 360 + 1)^4 \\
 &:= (1 + 4 + 8 - 35 + 4 + 8 + 360 - 1)^4 \\
 &:= (-1 + 4 + 8 - 35 + 4 + 8 + 360 + 1)^4 \\
 &:= (14 + 8 + 354 + 8 - 36 + 01)^4 \\
 &:= (1 + 483 + 5 + 4 - 83 - 60 - 1)^4 \\
 &:= (-1 + 483 + 5 + 4 - 83 - 60 + 1)^4 \\
 &:= (1 + 48 + 354 + 8 - 3 - 60 + 1)^4 \\
 &:= (-1 - 48 + 35 - 4 + 8 + 360 - 1)^4 \\
 &:= (1 + 48 + 3 - 54 - 8 + 360 - 1)^4 \\
 &:= (-1 + 48 + 3 - 54 - 8 + 360 + 1)^4 \\
 &:= (1 + 4 - 83 + 5 + 483 - 60 - 1)^4 \\
 &:= (-1 + 4 - 83 + 5 + 483 - 60 + 1)^4 \\
 &:= (-1 - 4 + 8 + 35 - 48 + 360 - 1)^4 \\
 &:= (148 + 3 + 54 + 83 + 60 + 1)^4 \\
 &**14850655912** := (1485 + 06 + 55 + 912)^3 \\
 &**14923275128** := (149 + 2327 - 5 + 1 - 2 - 8)^3 \\
 &:= (-1 + 4 + 9 + 2327 - 5 + 128)^3 \\
 &**14937972841** := (1 + 49379 + 72841)^2
 \end{aligned}$$

14959673344 := (1495 + 967 - 3 - 3 + 4 + 4) ³	:= (1 + 5 + 352 - 2 + 01 + 2 - 1 - 6) ⁴
14977894625 := (1497 + 7 + 8 + 946 + 2 + 5) ³	:= (1 + 5 + 352 + 2 - 01 - 2 + 1 - 6) ⁴
:= (1497 + 7 + 894 + 62 + 5) ³	:= (-1 + 5 + 352 + 2 + 01 - 2 + 1 - 6) ⁴
15124197817 := (-15 - 1 + 2419 + 78 - 1 - 7) ³	:= (1 + 5 + 352 - 2 - 01 + 2 + 1 - 6) ⁴
:= (1 + 51 + 2419 - 7 - 8 + 17) ³	:= (-1 + 5 + 352 - 2 + 01 + 2 + 1 - 6) ⁴
:= (-1 - 5 - 1 + 2419 + 78 - 17) ³	:= (1 - 5 + 352 + 2 - 01 - 2 - 1 + 6) ⁴
15142552424 := (1 + 51 - 4 + 2 + 5 - 5 + 2424) ³	:= (-1 - 5 + 352 + 2 + 01 - 2 - 1 + 6) ⁴
:= (1 + 51 - 4 + 2 - 5 + 5 + 2424) ³	:= (1 - 5 + 352 - 2 - 01 + 2 - 1 + 6) ⁴
:= (-1 - 5 - 1 + 4 - 2 + 55 + 2424) ³	:= (-1 - 5 + 352 - 2 + 01 + 2 - 1 + 6) ⁴
:= (1 - 5 + 1 - 4 + 2 + 55 + 2424) ³	:= (-1 - 5 + 352 + 2 - 01 - 2 + 1 + 6) ⁴
:= (15 + 1 + 4 + 25 + 5 + 2424) ³	:= (1 - 5 + 352 - 2 + 01 - 2 + 1 + 6) ⁴
:= (1 + 5 + 14 + 25 + 5 + 2424) ³	:= (-1 - 5 + 352 - 2 - 01 + 2 + 1 + 6) ⁴
15160921875 := (-1 - 5 + 1609 - 2 - 1 + 875) ³	:= (153 + 5 + 2 + 201 - 2 - 1 - 6) ⁴
:= (-1 - 5 - 1 + 609 - 2 + 1875) ³	:= (153 + 5 - 2 + 201 + 2 - 1 - 6) ⁴
15178486401 := (1 + 5 - 1 + 7 - 8 - 48 - 6 + 401) ⁴	:= (153 - 5 - 2 + 201 - 2 + 1 + 6) ⁴
:= (-1 + 5 + 1 + 7 - 8 - 48 - 6 + 401) ⁴	:= (15 + 352 + 2 - 012 + 1 - 6) ⁴
:= (-1 + 5 - 1 - 7 + 8 - 48 - 6 + 401) ⁴	:= (-15 + 352 - 2 + 012 - 1 + 6) ⁴
:= (1 + 5 + 1 - 7 - 8 - 48 + 6 + 401) ⁴	:= (15 + 352 + 2 + 01 - 2 - 16) ⁴
:= (-1 - 5 - 1 + 7 - 8 - 48 + 6 + 401) ⁴	:= (15 + 352 - 2 + 01 + 2 - 16) ⁴
:= (-15 - 17 - 8 + 4 - 8 - 6 + 401) ⁴	:= (-15 + 352 + 2 - 01 - 2 + 16) ⁴
:= (1 + 517 - 84 - 86 + 4 - 01) ⁴	:= (-15 + 352 - 2 - 01 + 2 + 16) ⁴
:= (-1 + 517 - 84 - 86 + 4 + 01) ⁴	:= (1 + 5 + 352 + 20 + 1 - 21 - 6) ⁴
:= (1 - 517 + 8 - 4 + 864 - 01) ⁴	:= (1 + 5 + 352 - 20 - 1 + 21 - 6) ⁴
:= (-1 - 517 + 8 - 4 + 864 + 01) ⁴	:= (-1 + 5 + 352 - 20 + 1 + 21 - 6) ⁴
:= (-1 - 51 - 78 + 486 - 4 - 01) ⁴	:= (1 - 5 + 352 + 20 - 1 - 21 + 6) ⁴
:= (15 + 17 - 84 + 8 - 6 + 401) ⁴	:= (-1 - 5 + 352 + 20 + 1 - 21 + 6) ⁴
:= (15 + 17 + 8 - 4 - 86 + 401) ⁴	:= (-1 - 5 + 352 - 20 - 1 + 21 + 6) ⁴
:= (-15 - 1 - 78 + 486 - 40 - 1) ⁴	:= (1 + 5 + 352 - 2 + 012 - 16) ⁴
:= (-15 + 1 - 78 + 48 - 6 + 401) ⁴	:= (-1 - 5 + 352 + 2 - 012 + 16) ⁴
:= (-1 + 5 - 178 + 486 + 40 - 1) ⁴	:= (-153 + 522 - 012 + 1 - 6) ⁴
:= (151 - 7 + 848 - 640 - 1) ⁴	:= (-153 + 522 + 01 - 2 - 16) ⁴
15179306176 := (1517 + 930 + 6 + 17 + 6) ³	:= (153 + 5 + 220 + 1 - 21 - 6) ⁴
:= (-1 - 517 + 9 + 3061 - 76) ³	:= (153 - 5 + 220 - 1 - 21 + 6) ⁴
15289924168 := (1 - 5 - 2 + 89 - 9 + 2416 - 8) ³	:= (15 + 352 - 20 + 12 - 1 - 6) ⁴
:= (-15 - 2 - 8 + 99 + 2416 - 8) ³	:= (-15 + 352 + 20 - 12 + 1 + 6) ⁴
15308412587 := (-153 + 08 + 41 + 2587) ³	:= (15 - 3 + 5 + 220 + 121 - 6) ⁴
:= (-15 + 3084 - 1 + 2 - 587) ³	:= (1 + 535 + 2 - 201 + 21 - 6) ⁴
:= (1530 + 841 + 25 + 87) ³	:= (153 + 52 + 20 + 121 + 6) ⁴
15352201216 := (1 + 5 + 352 + 2 + 01 - 2 - 1 - 6) ⁴	:= (15 + 352 + 201 - 216) ⁴
:= (-1 + 5 + 352 + 2 - 01 + 2 - 1 - 6) ⁴	:= (-15 + 352 - 201 + 216) ⁴

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{15382515303} &:= (-1 + 5 - 38 + 2515 + 3 + 03)^3 \\ &:= (-1 - 5 + 3 + 8 + 2515 - 30 - 3)^3 \\ &:= (-1 + 5 + 3 - 8 + 2515 - 30 + 3)^3 \\ &:= (-1 - 5 - 3 + 8 + 2515 - 30 + 3)^3 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{15386239549} &:= (1 + 5 + 3 + 86 + 2 + 3 + 9 + 5 + 4 - 9)^5 \\ &:= (1 + 5 + 3 + 86 + 2 + 3 + 9 - 5 - 4 + 9)^5 \\ &:= (1 + 5 + 3 + 86 - 2 - 3 + 9 + 5 - 4 + 9)^5 \\ &:= (1 + 5 - 3 + 86 - 2 + 3 + 9 + 5 - 4 + 9)^5 \\ &:= (1 - 5 + 3 + 86 + 2 + 3 + 9 + 5 - 4 + 9)^5 \\ &:= (-1 + 5 + 3 + 86 + 2 - 3 + 9 - 5 + 4 + 9)^5 \\ &:= (-1 + 5 - 3 + 86 + 2 + 3 + 9 - 5 + 4 + 9)^5 \\ &:= (1 + 5 + 3 + 86 + 2 + 3 - 9 + 5 + 4 + 9)^5 \\ &:= (-1 + 5 - 3 + 86 - 2 - 3 + 9 + 5 + 4 + 9)^5 \\ &:= (-1 - 5 + 3 + 86 + 2 - 3 + 9 + 5 + 4 + 9)^5 \\ &:= (-1 - 5 - 3 + 86 + 2 + 3 + 9 + 5 + 4 + 9)^5 \\ &:= (1 + 5 + 3 + 8 + 62 + 3 + 9 + 5 + 4 + 9)^5 \\ &:= (15 + 3 + 8 + 6 - 2 - 3 + 95 - 4 - 9)^5 \\ &:= (15 - 3 + 8 + 6 - 2 + 3 + 95 - 4 - 9)^5 \\ &:= (15 + 3 + 8 - 6 + 2 - 3 + 95 + 4 - 9)^5 \\ &:= (15 - 3 + 8 - 6 + 2 + 3 + 95 + 4 - 9)^5 \\ &:= (15 - 3 + 8 - 6 - 2 - 3 + 95 - 4 + 9)^5 \\ &:= (15 - 3 - 8 + 6 + 2 - 3 + 95 - 4 + 9)^5 \\ &:= (15 + 3 - 8 - 6 + 2 + 3 + 95 - 4 + 9)^5 \\ &:= (-15 + 3 + 8 + 6 + 2 - 3 + 95 + 4 + 9)^5 \\ &:= (-15 - 3 + 8 + 6 + 2 + 3 + 95 + 4 + 9)^5 \\ &:= (15 + 3 + 8 + 6 + 2 + 3 + 9 + 54 + 9)^5 \\ &:= (1 + 53 + 8 + 6 + 2 + 39 + 5 + 4 - 9)^5 \\ &:= (1 + 53 + 8 + 6 + 2 + 39 - 5 - 4 + 9)^5 \\ &:= (-1 + 53 + 8 - 6 - 2 + 39 + 5 + 4 + 9)^5 \\ &:= (-1 + 53 - 8 + 6 + 2 + 39 + 5 + 4 + 9)^5 \\ &:= (1 + 53 + 8 + 6 + 2 + 3 - 9 + 54 - 9)^5 \\ &:= (1 + 53 + 8 - 6 + 2 - 3 + 9 + 54 - 9)^5 \\ &:= (-1 + 53 + 8 - 6 - 2 + 3 + 9 + 54 - 9)^5 \\ &:= (-1 + 53 - 8 + 6 + 2 + 3 + 9 + 54 - 9)^5 \\ &:= (1 + 53 + 8 - 6 + 2 - 3 - 9 + 54 + 9)^5 \\ &:= (-1 + 53 + 8 - 6 - 2 + 3 - 9 + 54 + 9)^5 \\ &:= (-1 + 53 - 8 + 6 + 2 + 3 - 9 + 54 + 9)^5 \\ &:= (-1 + 53 - 8 - 6 + 2 - 3 + 9 + 54 + 9)^5 \\ &:= (1 + 5 + 38 + 6 + 2 + 39 + 5 + 4 + 9)^5 \\ &:= (1 - 5 + 38 - 6 + 2 - 3 + 95 - 4 - 9)^5 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} &:= (-1 - 5 + 38 - 6 - 2 + 3 + 95 - 4 - 9)^5 \\ &:= (1 + 5 + 38 + 6 + 2 + 3 + 9 + 54 - 9)^5 \\ &:= (1 + 5 + 38 + 6 + 2 + 3 - 9 + 54 + 9)^5 \\ &:= (1 + 5 + 38 - 6 + 2 - 3 + 9 + 54 + 9)^5 \\ &:= (-1 - 5 + 38 + 6 + 2 - 3 + 9 + 54 + 9)^5 \\ &:= (-1 + 5 + 38 - 6 - 2 + 3 + 9 + 54 + 9)^5 \\ &:= (1 + 5 + 3 + 86 + 23 + 9 - 5 - 4 - 9)^5 \\ &:= (1 - 5 + 3 + 86 + 23 + 9 + 5 - 4 - 9)^5 \\ &:= (-1 + 5 - 3 + 86 + 23 + 9 - 5 + 4 - 9)^5 \\ &:= (1 + 5 + 3 + 86 + 23 - 9 + 5 + 4 - 9)^5 \\ &:= (-1 - 5 - 3 + 86 + 23 + 9 + 5 + 4 - 9)^5 \\ &:= (1 + 5 + 3 + 86 + 23 - 9 - 5 - 4 + 9)^5 \\ &:= (-1 - 5 - 3 + 86 + 23 + 9 - 5 - 4 + 9)^5 \\ &:= (1 - 5 + 3 + 86 + 23 - 9 + 5 - 4 + 9)^5 \\ &:= (-1 + 5 - 3 + 86 + 23 - 9 - 5 + 4 + 9)^5 \\ &:= (-1 - 5 - 3 + 86 + 23 - 9 + 5 + 4 + 9)^5 \\ &:= (1 - 5 - 3 + 86 - 2 - 3 - 9 - 5 + 49)^5 \\ &:= (-1 + 5 + 3 + 8 + 62 - 3 - 9 - 5 + 49)^5 \\ &:= (-1 + 5 - 3 + 8 + 62 + 3 - 9 - 5 + 49)^5 \\ &:= (1 - 5 + 3 - 8 + 62 + 3 + 9 - 5 + 49)^5 \\ &:= (-1 - 5 + 3 + 8 + 62 - 3 - 9 + 5 + 49)^5 \\ &:= (-1 + 5 + 3 - 8 + 62 + 3 - 9 + 5 + 49)^5 \\ &:= (-1 - 5 - 3 + 8 + 62 + 3 - 9 + 5 + 49)^5 \\ &:= (1 + 5 + 3 + 8 + 6 + 23 + 9 + 5 + 49)^5 \\ &:= (1 + 5 + 3 + 8 + 6 + 2 + 39 + 54 - 9)^5 \\ &:= (-1 + 5 + 3 + 8 - 6 - 2 + 39 + 54 + 9)^5 \\ &:= (1 + 5 - 3 + 8 - 6 + 2 + 39 + 54 + 9)^5 \\ &:= (-1 + 5 + 3 - 8 + 6 + 2 + 39 + 54 + 9)^5 \\ &:= (-1 - 5 - 3 + 8 + 6 + 2 + 39 + 54 + 9)^5 \\ &:= (153 - 8 + 6 - 23 - 9 - 5 + 4 - 9)^5 \\ &:= (153 + 8 + 6 + 2 + 3 - 9 - 5 - 49)^5 \\ &:= (153 + 8 - 6 + 2 - 3 + 9 - 5 - 49)^5 \\ &:= (153 + 8 + 6 - 2 - 3 - 9 + 5 - 49)^5 \\ &:= (153 - 8 - 6 + 2 + 3 + 9 + 5 - 49)^5 \\ &:= (15 + 38 + 62 + 3 + 9 - 5 - 4 - 9)^5 \\ &:= (15 + 38 + 62 + 3 - 9 + 5 + 4 - 9)^5 \\ &:= (15 + 38 + 62 + 3 - 9 - 5 - 4 + 9)^5 \\ &:= (-15 + 38 + 62 - 3 + 9 + 5 + 4 + 9)^5 \\ &:= (15 + 38 + 6 + 23 + 9 + 5 + 4 + 9)^5 \\ &:= (15 + 38 + 6 + 2 + 3 - 9 + 5 + 49)^5 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 &:= (15 + 38 - 6 + 2 - 3 + 9 + 5 + 49)^5 \\
 &:= (-15 - 3 + 86 + 2 + 39 + 5 + 4 - 9)^5 \\
 &:= (-15 - 3 + 86 + 2 + 39 - 5 - 4 + 9)^5 \\
 &:= (-15 + 3 + 86 + 2 - 3 - 9 + 54 - 9)^5 \\
 &:= (-15 - 3 + 86 + 2 + 3 - 9 + 54 - 9)^5 \\
 &:= (15 + 3 + 8 + 62 + 39 - 5 - 4 - 9)^5 \\
 &:= (-15 - 3 + 8 + 62 + 39 + 5 + 4 + 9)^5 \\
 &:= (-15 + 3 + 8 + 62 - 3 + 9 + 54 - 9)^5 \\
 &:= (-15 - 3 + 8 + 62 + 3 + 9 + 54 - 9)^5 \\
 &:= (-15 + 3 + 8 + 62 - 3 - 9 + 54 + 9)^5 \\
 &:= (-15 - 3 + 8 + 62 + 3 - 9 + 54 + 9)^5 \\
 &:= (15 + 3 - 8 - 6 + 23 + 95 - 4 - 9)^5 \\
 &:= (-15 - 3 + 8 + 6 + 23 + 95 + 4 - 9)^5 \\
 &:= (15 + 3 + 8 + 6 - 23 + 95 - 4 + 9)^5 \\
 &:= (-15 + 3 - 8 + 6 + 23 + 95 - 4 + 9)^5 \\
 &:= (15 + 3 + 8 + 6 + 23 + 9 + 54 - 9)^5 \\
 &:= (15 + 3 + 8 + 6 + 23 - 9 + 54 + 9)^5 \\
 &:= (15 - 3 + 8 - 6 + 23 + 9 + 54 + 9)^5 \\
 &:= (15 - 3 + 8 - 6 + 2 + 39 + 5 + 49)^5 \\
 &:= (1 + 53 + 86 - 2 - 39 + 5 - 4 + 9)^5 \\
 &:= (-1 + 53 + 86 + 2 - 39 - 5 + 4 + 9)^5 \\
 &:= (-1 - 53 + 86 - 2 - 3 + 95 - 4 - 9)^5 \\
 &:= (1 + 53 + 86 + 2 + 3 + 9 - 54 + 9)^5 \\
 &:= (-1 - 53 + 86 + 2 + 3 + 9 + 54 + 9)^5 \\
 &:= (-1 - 53 + 8 + 62 + 3 + 95 + 4 - 9)^5 \\
 &:= (-1 + 53 + 8 - 62 + 3 + 95 + 4 + 9)^5 \\
 &:= (-1 + 53 - 8 + 6 - 23 + 95 - 4 - 9)^5 \\
 &:= (-1 + 53 - 8 + 6 + 23 - 9 + 54 - 9)^5 \\
 &:= (1 + 53 + 8 + 6 - 2 - 3 + 95 - 49)^5 \\
 &:= (-1 - 53 + 8 + 6 + 2 + 3 + 95 + 49)^5 \\
 &:= (1 + 5 - 38 + 62 - 3 + 95 - 4 - 9)^5 \\
 &:= (1 + 5 + 38 + 6 - 23 + 95 - 4 - 9)^5 \\
 &:= (1 + 5 + 38 + 6 + 23 - 9 + 54 - 9)^5 \\
 &:= (1 - 5 + 38 - 6 - 2 + 39 - 5 + 49)^5 \\
 &:= (1 - 5 - 38 + 6 - 2 + 3 + 95 + 49)^5
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 &:= (-1 + 5 - 38 - 6 + 2 + 3 + 95 + 49)^5 \\
 &:= (1 - 5 - 3 + 86 - 23 + 9 - 5 + 49)^5 \\
 &:= (-1 + 5 - 3 + 86 - 23 - 9 + 5 + 49)^5 \\
 &:= (-1 + 5 - 3 + 86 - 2 - 39 + 54 + 9)^5 \\
 &:= (-1 - 5 + 3 + 86 + 2 - 39 + 54 + 9)^5 \\
 &:= (153 - 86 + 23 + 9 + 5 - 4 + 9)^5 \\
 &:= (153 - 8 - 6 + 23 - 9 + 5 - 49)^5 \\
 &:= (153 + 8 + 6 - 23 + 9 + 5 - 49)^5 \\
 &:= (-15 - 3 + 86 - 2 - 3 + 95 - 49)^5 \\
 &:= (15 - 3 - 8 + 62 - 3 + 95 - 49)^5 \\
 &:= (-1 - 53 - 86 + 239 + 5 - 4 + 9)^5 \\
 &:= (1 - 53 - 86 + 239 - 5 + 4 + 9)^5 \\
 &:= (-1 - 53 + 86 - 23 + 95 - 4 + 9)^5 \\
 &:= (1 + 53 + 86 + 23 + 9 - 54 - 9)^5 \\
 &:= (-1 - 53 + 86 + 23 + 9 + 54 - 9)^5 \\
 &:= (1 + 53 + 86 + 23 - 9 - 54 + 9)^5 \\
 &:= (-1 - 53 + 86 + 23 - 9 + 54 + 9)^5 \\
 &:= (-1 + 53 - 86 + 2 - 3 + 95 + 49)^5 \\
 &:= (1 + 53 + 8 + 62 + 39 - 5 - 49)^5 \\
 &:= (-1 - 53 + 8 + 62 + 39 + 5 + 49)^5 \\
 &:= (1 + 53 - 8 - 6 + 23 + 95 - 49)^5 \\
 &:= (-1 + 5 + 38 + 62 - 39 - 5 + 49)^5 \\
 &:= (-1 - 5 + 38 + 62 - 39 + 5 + 49)^5 \\
 &:= (1 - 5 + 38 + 6 + 23 + 95 - 49)^5 \\
 &:= (-1 + 5 - 3 - 86 + 239 - 54 + 9)^5 \\
 &:= (15 + 38 + 62 + 39 - 54 + 9)^5 \\
 &:= (-15 + 38 + 62 - 39 + 54 + 9)^5 \\
 &:= (15 + 3 + 8 + 623 + 9 - 549)^5 \\
 &:= (-1 + 53 - 8 + 623 - 9 - 549)^5 \\
 &:= (1 + 5 + 386 - 239 + 5 - 49)^5 \\
 &:= (1 + 5 + 38 + 623 - 9 - 549)^5 \\
 &:= (-153 + 86 + 239 - 54 - 9)^5 \\
 &:= (-153 - 86 + 2 + 395 - 49)^5
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 \mathbf{15392124225} &:= (-153 - 9 + 2 + 124225)^2 \\
 \mathbf{15438249000} &:= (15 - 4 - 3 - 8 + 2490 + 00)^3 \\
 &:= (-15 + 4 + 3 + 8 + 2490 + 00)^3 \\
 \mathbf{15527402881} &:= (15 + 52 - 7 + 4 + 0288 + 1)^4
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 &:= (-15 + 5 + 274 + 02 + 88 - 1)^4 \\
 &:= (-15 + 5 + 2 + 74 + 0288 - 1)^4 \\
 &:= (1 + 5 + 5 + 27 + 402 - 88 + 1)^4 \\
 &:= (-1 + 5 - 5 + 27 + 40 + 288 - 1)^4
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 & := (-1 - 5 + 5 + 27 + 40 + 288 - 1)^4 \\
 \mathbf{15625000000} & := (1 + 56 - 2 - 5 + 000000)^6 \\
 & := (1 - 5 + 6 - 2 + 50 + 00000)^6 \\
 & := (-1 + 5 - 6 + 2 + 50 + 00000)^6 \\
 & := (1 + 5 - 6 + 2500 + 0000)^3 \\
 & := (-1 - 5 + 6 + 2500 + 0000)^3 \\
 \mathbf{15681317527} & := (-1 + 5 - 681 + 3175 - 2 + 7)^3 \\
 & := (1 - 56 + 813 + 1752 - 7)^3 \\
 \mathbf{15704099856} & := (15 - 70 + 409 + 9 - 8 + 5 - 6)^4 \\
 & := (15 - 70 + 409 - 9 + 8 - 5 + 6)^4 \\
 & := (-1 - 5 - 7 + 0409 - 98 + 56)^4 \\
 & := (-1 + 5 - 704 + 0998 + 56)^4 \\
 \mathbf{15813251000} & := (1 - 5 + 8 - 1 - 3 + 2510 + 00)^3 \\
 & := (-1 - 5 + 8 + 1 - 3 + 2510 + 00)^3 \\
 & := (1 + 5 - 8 - 1 + 3 + 2510 + 00)^3 \\
 & := (-1 + 5 - 8 + 1 + 3 + 2510 + 00)^3 \\
 \mathbf{15882300625} & := (-1 - 5 - 8 + 82 + 300 - 6 - 2 - 5)^4 \\
 & := (1 - 5 + 8 - 8 + 2 + 300 + 62 - 5)^4 \\
 & := (1 - 5 - 8 + 8 + 2 + 300 + 62 - 5)^4 \\
 & := (1 + 5 - 8 - 8 - 2 + 300 + 62 + 5)^4 \\
 & := (1 + 5 + 8 + 8 + 2 + 300 + 6 + 25)^4 \\
 & := (1 + 5 + 88 + 230 + 06 + 25)^4 \\
 & := (1 - 5 + 88 + 2 + 300 - 6 - 25)^4 \\
 & := (1 - 5 + 8 + 82 + 300 - 6 - 25)^4 \\
 & := (-158 - 82 - 30 + 0625)^4 \\
 \mathbf{15888972744} & := (-158 - 88 + 9 + 7 + 2744)^3 \\
 \mathbf{15926924096} & := (1 + 5 + 92 + 6 + 9 + 2409 - 6)^3 \\
 & := (1 + 5 + 92 - 6 + 9 + 2409 + 6)^3 \\
 & := (-1 - 5 + 92 + 6 + 9 + 2409 + 6)^3 \\
 \mathbf{15945922413} & := (-1 + 5 + 94 - 5 + 9 + 2 + 2413)^3 \\
 & := (-1 - 5 + 94 + 5 + 9 + 2 + 2413)^3 \\
 & := (-1 + 5 + 9 + 4 - 5 + 92 + 2413)^3 \\
 & := (-1 - 5 + 9 + 4 + 5 + 92 + 2413)^3 \\
 & := (1594 - 5 + 922 + 4 - 1 + 3)^3 \\
 \mathbf{15964935832} & := (1596 - 4 + 935 - 8 - 3 + 2)^3 \\
 \mathbf{16062013696} & := (-16 + 06 + 2 + 01 + 369 - 6)^4 \\
 & := (-16 - 06 + 2 + 01 + 369 + 6)^4 \\
 & := (-160 + 620 + 1 - 3 - 6 - 96)^4
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 \mathbf{16079333824} & := (1607 + 93 + 3 - 3 + 824)^3 \\
 & := (1607 + 93 - 3 + 3 + 824)^3 \\
 & := (-1 - 60 - 793 + 3382 - 4)^3 \\
 \mathbf{16105100000} & := (161 - 051 + 00000)^5 \\
 & := (16 - 1 - 05 + 100 + 000)^5 \\
 & := (1 - 6 + 105 + 10 + 0000)^5 \\
 & := (-1 + 6 + 10 - 5 + 100 + 000)^5 \\
 & := (1 - 6 + 10 + 5 + 100 + 000)^5 \\
 \mathbf{16117587576} & := (16 + 1 + 1758 + 757 - 6)^3 \\
 \mathbf{16121126961} & := (1 - 6 + 12 + 1 + 126961)^2 \\
 \mathbf{16136737183} & := (1613 - 6 + 737 + 183)^3 \\
 \mathbf{16155901952} & := (16 + 1559 + 01 + 952)^3 \\
 & := (16 + 1 + 559 + 01952)^3 \\
 \mathbf{16175081889} & := (1617 + 5 + 0818 + 89)^3 \\
 \mathbf{16232712768} & := (-162 + 3 + 2712 - 7 - 6 - 8)^3 \\
 \mathbf{16243247601} & := (1 + 6 + 24 + 324 + 7 - 6 + 01)^4 \\
 & := (1 - 6 + 24 + 324 + 7 + 6 + 01)^4 \\
 & := (1 - 6 + 2 + 432 - 4 - 7 - 60 - 1)^4 \\
 & := (-1 - 6 + 2 + 432 - 4 - 7 - 60 + 1)^4 \\
 & := (-1 + 6 - 24 + 324 - 7 + 60 - 1)^4 \\
 & := (162 + 4 + 3 + 247 - 60 + 1)^4 \\
 & := (1 - 62 + 432 + 47 - 60 - 1)^4 \\
 & := (-1 - 62 + 432 + 47 - 60 + 1)^4 \\
 & := (16 - 243 - 24 + 7 + 601)^4 \\
 \mathbf{16251953437} & := (16 + 2519 - 5 + 3 + 4 + 3 - 7)^3 \\
 & := (16 + 2519 - 5 + 3 - 4 - 3 + 7)^3 \\
 & := (16 + 2519 - 5 - 3 - 4 + 3 + 7)^3 \\
 & := (1 - 6 + 2519 - 5 + 34 - 3 - 7)^3 \\
 & := (16 + 2519 - 5 - 34 + 37)^3 \\
 \mathbf{16271209304} & := (1627 + 1 - 20 + 930 - 4)^3 \\
 \mathbf{16329068153} & := (1632 + 906 + 8 - 1 - 5 - 3)^3 \\
 & := (1632 + 906 - 8 - 1 + 5 + 3)^3 \\
 \mathbf{16367716819} & := (1636 + 77 + 1 + 6 + 819)^3 \\
 & := (1636 + 7 + 71 + 6 + 819)^3 \\
 \mathbf{16406426421} & := (-164 + 064 + 2642 - 1)^3 \\
 \mathbf{16426010896} & := (1 + 6 + 4 + 260 - 1 - 08 + 96)^4 \\
 & := (-1 + 6 + 4 + 260 + 1 - 08 + 96)^4 \\
 & := (16 + 426 - 01 - 089 + 6)^4
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 &:= (1 + 64 + 260 + 10 + 8 + 9 + 6)^4 & &:= (-1 - 6 + 8 + 5 + 058 + 1 - 5 + 51)^5 \\
 &:= (-1 + 6 + 426 + 010 - 89 + 6)^4 & &:= (1 - 6 + 8 - 5 + 058 - 1 + 5 + 51)^5 \\
 &:= (16 + 4 + 260 - 10 - 8 + 96)^4 & &:= (-1 - 6 + 8 - 5 + 058 + 1 + 5 + 51)^5 \\
 &:= (1 + 64 - 2 - 601 + 0896)^4 & &:= (168 - 50 - 5 + 8 + 1 - 5 - 5 - 1)^5 \\
 \mathbf{16542390592} &:= (1 + 6 + 54 + 2390 + 5 + 92)^3 & &:= (168 - 50 - 5 + 8 - 1 - 5 - 5 + 1)^5 \\
 \mathbf{16610312161} &:= (-1 + 66 - 10 + 312 - 1 - 6 - 1)^4 & &:= (168 - 5 - 05 + 8 + 1 - 55 - 1)^5 \\
 &:= (-1 + 66 - 1 + 0312 - 16 - 1)^4 & &:= (168 - 5 - 05 + 8 - 1 - 55 + 1)^5 \\
 &:= (166 - 1 + 031 + 2 + 161)^4 & &:= (168 - 5 - 05 + 8 + 1 - 5 - 51)^5 \\
 &:= (16 + 6 + 10 + 312 + 16 - 1)^4 & &:= (-16 + 85 - 05 - 8 + 1 + 55 - 1)^5 \\
 &:= (1 - 6 + 610 - 31 - 216 + 1)^4 & &:= (-16 + 85 - 05 - 8 - 1 + 55 + 1)^5 \\
 \mathbf{16620420608} &:= (-1662 + 04206 + 08)^3 & &:= (-16 + 85 + 05 - 8 - 1 - 5 + 51)^5 \\
 \mathbf{16679103875} &:= (1667 + 9 + 1 + 03 + 875)^3 & &:= (-16 + 85 - 05 - 8 - 1 + 5 + 51)^5 \\
 \mathbf{16698695616} &:= (1669 + 869 + 5 + 6 + 1 + 6)^3 & &:= (-16 - 8 + 50 + 5 + 81 + 5 - 5 - 1)^5 \\
 \mathbf{16737925112} &:= (1 + 67 - 3 - 7 - 9 + 2511 - 2)^3 & &:= (-16 - 8 + 50 + 5 + 81 - 5 + 5 - 1)^5 \\
 \mathbf{16836267547} &:= (-168 + 3 + 6 + 2675 + 47)^3 & &:= (-16 - 8 + 50 - 5 + 81 + 5 + 5 - 1)^5 \\
 \mathbf{16850581551} &:= (-1 + 6 + 85 + 05 + 8 - 1 + 5 + 5 - 1)^5 & &:= (-16 - 8 + 5 - 05 + 81 + 55 - 1)^5 \\
 &:= (1 + 6 + 8 + 50 + 58 - 1 - 5 - 5 - 1)^5 & &:= (-16 - 8 - 5 + 05 + 81 + 55 - 1)^5 \\
 &:= (-1 + 6 + 8 + 50 + 58 + 1 - 5 - 5 - 1)^5 & &:= (1 + 68 + 50 + 5 + 8 - 15 - 5 - 1)^5 \\
 &:= (1 - 6 + 8 + 50 + 58 + 1 + 5 - 5 - 1)^5 & &:= (1 + 68 + 50 - 5 + 8 - 15 + 5 - 1)^5 \\
 &:= (1 - 6 + 8 + 50 + 58 + 1 - 5 + 5 - 1)^5 & &:= (-1 + 68 + 50 + 5 + 8 - 15 - 5 + 1)^5 \\
 &:= (-1 + 6 + 8 + 50 + 58 - 1 - 5 - 5 + 1)^5 & &:= (-1 + 68 + 50 - 5 + 8 - 15 + 5 + 1)^5 \\
 &:= (1 - 6 + 8 + 50 + 58 - 1 + 5 - 5 + 1)^5 & &:= (1 + 68 + 5 + 058 - 15 - 5 - 1)^5 \\
 &:= (-1 - 6 + 8 + 50 + 58 + 1 + 5 - 5 + 1)^5 & &:= (1 + 68 - 5 + 058 - 15 + 5 - 1)^5 \\
 &:= (1 - 6 + 8 + 50 + 58 - 1 - 5 + 5 + 1)^5 & &:= (-1 + 68 + 5 + 058 - 15 - 5 + 1)^5 \\
 &:= (-1 - 6 + 8 + 50 + 58 + 1 - 5 + 5 + 1)^5 & &:= (-1 + 68 - 5 + 058 - 15 + 5 + 1)^5 \\
 &:= (1 - 6 + 8 + 50 - 5 + 8 + 1 + 55 - 1)^5 & &:= (-1 + 68 + 5 - 05 + 8 - 15 + 51)^5 \\
 &:= (1 - 6 + 8 + 50 - 5 + 8 - 1 + 55 + 1)^5 & &:= (-1 + 68 - 5 + 05 + 8 - 15 + 51)^5 \\
 &:= (-1 - 6 + 8 + 50 - 5 + 8 + 1 + 55 + 1)^5 & &:= (-1 - 6 + 85 + 05 - 8 - 15 + 51)^5 \\
 &:= (-1 + 6 + 8 + 50 - 5 + 8 - 1 - 5 + 51)^5 & &:= (16 + 8 + 50 + 58 - 15 - 5 - 1)^5 \\
 &:= (1 - 6 + 8 + 50 + 5 + 8 - 1 - 5 + 51)^5 & &:= (-16 + 8 + 50 + 58 + 15 - 5 + 1)^5 \\
 &:= (-1 - 6 + 8 + 50 + 5 + 8 + 1 - 5 + 51)^5 & &:= (16 - 8 - 50 + 5 - 8 + 155 + 1)^5 \\
 &:= (1 - 6 + 8 + 50 - 5 + 8 - 1 + 5 + 51)^5 & &:= (-16 + 8 - 50 + 5 + 8 + 155 + 1)^5 \\
 &:= (-1 - 6 + 8 + 50 - 5 + 8 + 1 + 5 + 51)^5 & &:= (16 - 8 + 50 - 5 - 8 + 15 + 51)^5 \\
 &:= (1 - 6 + 8 - 5 + 058 + 1 + 55 - 1)^5 & &:= (-16 + 8 + 50 - 5 + 8 + 15 + 51)^5 \\
 &:= (1 - 6 + 8 - 5 + 058 - 1 + 55 + 1)^5 & &:= (16 - 8 + 5 - 058 + 155 + 1)^5 \\
 &:= (-1 - 6 + 8 - 5 + 058 + 1 + 55 + 1)^5 & &:= (-16 + 8 - 5 + 058 + 15 + 51)^5 \\
 &:= (-1 + 6 + 8 - 5 + 058 - 1 - 5 + 51)^5 & &:= (-1 - 68 + 50 - 5 + 81 + 55 - 1)^5 \\
 &:= (1 - 6 + 8 + 5 + 058 - 1 - 5 + 51)^5 & &:= (-16 - 85 + 058 + 155 - 1)^5
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} &:= (1 + 68 + 50 + 58 - 15 - 51)^5 & &:= (-1 + 6 + 9 - 8 - 3 - 5 - 6 + 30 - 4 + 1)^8 \\ &:= (-1 + 68 - 50 + 58 - 15 + 51)^5 & &:= (1 + 6 - 9 + 8 - 3 - 5 - 6 + 30 - 4 + 1)^8 \\ \mathbf{16855982144} &:= (1685 + 5 + 9 + 821 + 44)^3 & &:= (1 - 6 + 9 - 8 - 3 + 5 - 6 + 30 - 4 + 1)^8 \\ \mathbf{16901300025} &:= (1 + 6 - 9 + 0130002 + 5)^2 & &:= (1 + 6 - 9 - 8 + 3 + 5 - 6 + 30 - 4 + 1)^8 \\ \mathbf{16913002500} &:= (16 + 9 + 130025 + 00)^2 & &:= (-1 - 6 + 9 - 8 - 3 - 5 + 6 + 30 - 4 + 1)^8 \\ \mathbf{16915218263} &:= (1691 + 52 + 1 + 826 - 3)^3 & &:= (1 - 6 - 9 + 8 - 3 - 5 + 6 + 30 - 4 + 1)^8 \\ \mathbf{16915218263} &:= (1 + 691 + 52 + 1826 - 3)^3 & &:= (-1 + 6 - 9 - 8 + 3 - 5 + 6 + 30 - 4 + 1)^8 \\ \mathbf{16983563041} &:= (16 + 9 - 8 + 3 - 5 + 6 + 3 - 04 - 1)^8 & &:= (1 - 6 - 9 - 8 + 3 + 5 + 6 + 30 - 4 + 1)^8 \\ &:= (16 + 9 + 8 - 3 - 5 - 6 - 3 + 04 - 1)^8 & &:= (-1 - 6 - 9 + 8 + 3 - 5 - 6 + 30 + 4 + 1)^8 \\ &:= (16 + 9 - 8 + 3 + 5 - 6 - 3 + 04 - 1)^8 & &:= (-1 + 6 - 9 - 8 - 3 + 5 - 6 + 30 + 4 + 1)^8 \\ &:= (16 - 9 + 8 + 3 - 5 + 6 - 3 + 04 - 1)^8 & &:= (-1 - 6 - 9 - 8 - 3 + 5 + 6 + 30 + 4 + 1)^8 \\ &:= (16 + 9 - 8 - 3 + 5 - 6 + 3 + 04 - 1)^8 & &:= (-16 - 9 - 8 - 3 - 5 + 63 - 04 + 1)^8 \\ &:= (16 - 9 + 8 - 3 - 5 + 6 + 3 + 04 - 1)^8 & &:= (-16 + 9 - 8 - 3 + 5 - 6 - 3 + 041)^8 \\ &:= (16 - 9 - 8 + 3 + 5 + 6 + 3 + 04 - 1)^8 & &:= (-16 - 9 + 8 - 3 - 5 + 6 - 3 + 041)^8 \\ &:= (16 + 9 + 8 + 3 - 5 - 6 - 3 - 04 + 1)^8 & &:= (-16 - 9 - 8 + 3 + 5 + 6 - 3 + 041)^8 \\ &:= (16 + 9 - 8 - 3 + 5 + 6 - 3 - 04 + 1)^8 & &:= (-16 - 9 + 8 + 3 - 5 - 6 + 3 + 041)^8 \\ &:= (16 + 9 + 8 - 3 - 5 - 6 + 3 - 04 + 1)^8 & &:= (-16 - 9 - 8 - 3 + 5 + 6 + 3 + 041)^8 \\ &:= (16 + 9 - 8 + 3 + 5 - 6 + 3 - 04 + 1)^8 & &:= (1 + 69 - 8 - 35 - 6 + 3 - 04 - 1)^8 \\ &:= (16 - 9 + 8 + 3 - 5 + 6 + 3 - 04 + 1)^8 & &:= (-1 + 69 - 8 - 35 - 6 - 3 + 04 - 1)^8 \\ &:= (16 - 9 + 8 + 3 + 5 - 6 - 3 + 04 + 1)^8 & &:= (-1 + 69 - 8 - 35 - 6 + 3 - 04 + 1)^8 \\ &:= (16 - 9 + 8 - 3 + 5 - 6 + 3 + 04 + 1)^8 & &:= (1 + 69 + 8 - 3 - 56 - 3 + 04 - 1)^8 \\ &:= (-1 - 6 - 9 + 8 + 35 - 6 + 3 - 04 - 1)^8 & &:= (1 + 69 + 8 + 3 - 56 - 3 - 04 + 1)^8 \\ &:= (1 + 6 - 9 - 8 + 35 - 6 - 3 + 04 - 1)^8 & &:= (1 + 69 + 8 - 3 - 56 + 3 - 04 + 1)^8 \\ &:= (1 - 6 - 9 - 8 + 35 + 6 - 3 + 04 - 1)^8 & &:= (-1 + 69 + 8 - 3 - 56 - 3 + 04 + 1)^8 \\ &:= (1 - 6 + 9 - 8 + 35 - 6 - 3 - 04 + 1)^8 & &:= (1 + 69 - 8 + 3 - 5 - 6 - 30 - 4 - 1)^8 \\ &:= (1 + 6 - 9 - 8 + 35 - 6 + 3 - 04 + 1)^8 & &:= (-1 + 69 - 8 - 3 - 5 - 6 - 30 + 4 - 1)^8 \\ &:= (1 - 6 - 9 - 8 + 35 + 6 + 3 - 04 + 1)^8 & &:= (-1 + 69 - 8 + 3 - 5 - 6 - 30 - 4 + 1)^8 \\ &:= (-1 + 6 - 9 - 8 + 35 - 6 - 3 + 04 + 1)^8 & &:= (1 - 6 + 98 - 3 - 5 - 63 - 04 + 1)^8 \\ &:= (-1 - 6 - 9 - 8 + 35 + 6 - 3 + 04 + 1)^8 & &:= (1 - 6 - 9 + 83 - 56 + 3 + 04 - 1)^8 \\ &:= (1 + 6 + 9 - 8 - 3 - 5 - 6 + 30 - 4 - 1)^8 & &:= (1 + 6 - 9 + 83 - 56 - 3 - 04 + 1)^8 \\ &:= (-1 - 6 - 9 + 8 + 3 + 5 - 6 + 30 - 4 - 1)^8 & &:= (-1 - 6 - 9 + 83 - 56 + 3 + 04 + 1)^8 \\ &:= (1 - 6 + 9 - 8 - 3 - 5 + 6 + 30 - 4 - 1)^8 & &:= (1 - 6 + 9 - 8 - 35 + 63 - 04 - 1)^8 \\ &:= (1 + 6 - 9 - 8 + 3 - 5 + 6 + 30 - 4 - 1)^8 & &:= (-1 + 6 - 9 - 8 - 35 + 63 + 04 - 1)^8 \\ &:= (-1 - 6 + 9 - 8 + 3 - 5 - 6 + 30 + 4 - 1)^8 & &:= (-1 - 6 + 9 - 8 - 35 + 63 - 04 + 1)^8 \\ &:= (1 - 6 - 9 + 8 + 3 - 5 - 6 + 30 + 4 - 1)^8 & &:= (1 - 6 - 9 + 8 - 35 + 63 - 04 + 1)^8 \\ &:= (1 + 6 - 9 - 8 - 3 + 5 - 6 + 30 + 4 - 1)^8 & &:= (-1 + 6 + 9 + 8 + 35 + 6 - 3 - 041)^8 \\ &:= (-1 + 6 - 9 - 8 - 3 - 5 + 6 + 30 + 4 - 1)^8 & &:= (-1 + 6 + 9 + 8 - 35 - 6 - 3 + 041)^8 \\ &:= (1 - 6 - 9 - 8 - 3 + 5 + 6 + 30 + 4 - 1)^8 & &:= (-1 - 6 + 9 + 8 - 35 + 6 - 3 + 041)^8 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} & := (-1+7-1+72-5+299-3-6)^4 & := (17+1-7-9-8+6+9-1-8+4)^{17} \\ & := (1-7+1+72+5+299-3-6)^4 & := (-17+1+7+9-8+6+9-1-8+4)^{34} \\ & := (1-7-1+72-5+299-3+6)^4 & := (-17-1-7+9+8+6+9-1-8+4)^{34} \\ & := (-1-7+1+72-5+299-3+6)^4 & := (-17+1-7+9+8+6+9-1-8+4)^{17} \\ & := (1+7-1+7+252+99+3-6)^4 & := (17-1+7-9+8-6-9+1-8+4)^{17} \\ & := (-1+7+1+7+252+99+3-6)^4 & := (17+1+7-9-8+6-9+1-8+4)^{34} \\ & := (1+7+1-7+252+99+3+6)^4 & := (17-1-7+9-8+6-9+1-8+4)^{17} \\ & := (1-7+1+7+252+99+3+6)^4 & := (17-1-7-9+8+6-9+1-8+4)^{34} \\ & := (1+7-1+7+252+9+93-6)^4 & := (17+1-7-9+8+6-9+1-8+4)^{17} \\ & := (-1+7+1+7+252+9+93-6)^4 & := (-17+1+7+9+8+6-9+1-8+4)^{34} \\ & := (1+7+1-7+252+9+93+6)^4 & := (17-1-7-9-8+6+9+1-8+4)^{17} \\ & := (1-7+1+7+252+9+93+6)^4 & := (-17-1+7+9-8+6+9+1-8+4)^{34} \\ & := (1+71+7-25+299+3+6)^4 & := (-17+1+7+9-8+6+9+1-8+4)^{17} \\ & := (1+7+1-7+25+299+36)^4 & := (-17+1+7-9+8+6+9+1-8+4)^{34} \\ & := (1-7+1+7+25+299+36)^4 & := (-17-1-7+9+8+6+9+1-8+4)^{17} \\ & := (171-7+252-9-9-36)^4 & := (17-1+7-9-8-6-9-1+8+4)^{34} \\ & := (17-172+529-9+3-6)^4 & := (17+1+7-9-8-6-9-1+8+4)^{17} \\ & := (17+17-2-5+299+36)^4 & := (17-1-7-9+8-6-9-1+8+4)^{17} \\ & := (-17-1-7+252+99+36)^4 & := (-17-1+7+9+8-6-9-1+8+4)^{34} \\ & := (-1+717-252-99+3-6)^4 & := (-17+1+7+9+8-6-9-1+8+4)^{17} \\ & := (-1-7-17+252+99+36)^4 & := (17+1-7-9-8+6-9-1+8+4)^{34} \\ \mathbf{17179869184} & := (17+1-7+9-8-6+9-1-8-4)^{34} & := (-17+1-7+9+8+6-9-1+8+4)^{34} \\ & := (17+1-7+9+8-6-9+1-8-4)^{34} & := (-17-1+7+9-8-6+9-1+8+4)^{17} \\ & := (17-1-7+9-8-6+9+1-8-4)^{34} & := (-17-1+7-9+8-6+9-1+8+4)^{34} \\ & := (17+1-7+9-8-6+9+1-8-4)^{17} & := (-17+1+7-9+8-6+9-1+8+4)^{17} \\ & := (17+1-7-9+8-6+9+1-8-4)^{34} & := (-17-1-7+9-8+6+9-1+8+4)^{34} \\ & := (17+1-7+9-8-6-9+1+8-4)^{34} & := (-17+1-7+9-8+6+9-1+8+4)^{17} \\ & := (17+1-7-9-8-6+9+1+8-4)^{34} & := (-17+1-7-9+8+6+9-1+8+4)^{34} \\ & := (-17+1-7+9+8-6+9+1+8-4)^{34} & := (17-1+7-9-8-6-9+1+8+4)^{17} \\ & := (17-1+7+9-8-6-9-1-8+4)^{17} & := (-17-1+7+9+8-6-9+1+8+4)^{17} \\ & := (17-1+7-9+8-6-9-1-8+4)^{34} & := (17-1-7-9-8+6-9+1+8+4)^{34} \\ & := (17+1+7-9+8-6-9-1-8+4)^{17} & := (17+1-7-9-8+6-9+1+8+4)^{17} \\ & := (17-1-7+9-8+6-9-1-8+4)^{34} & := (-17+1+7+9-8+6-9+1+8+4)^{34} \\ & := (17+1-7+9-8+6-9-1-8+4)^{17} & := (-17-1-7+9+8+6-9+1+8+4)^{34} \\ & := (17+1-7-9+8+6-9-1-8+4)^{34} & := (-17+1-7+9+8+6-9+1+8+4)^{17} \\ & := (17-1+7-9-8-6+9-1-8+4)^{17} & := (-17-1+7-9+8-6+9+1+8+4)^{17} \\ & := (-17-1+7+9+8-6+9-1-8+4)^{17} & := (-17+1+7-9-8+6+9+1+8+4)^{34} \\ & := (17-1-7-9-8+6+9-1-8+4)^{34} & := (-17-1-7+9-8+6+9+1+8+4)^{17} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} & := (-17-1-7-9+8+6+9+1+8+4)^{34} & := (1+7-17+9+8-6-9-1+8+4)^{17} \\ & := (-17+1-7-9+8+6+9+1+8+4)^{17} & := (1-7+17-9-8+6-9-1+8+4)^{34} \\ & := (1-7+17+9-8-6+9-1-8-4)^{34} & := (1-7-17+9+8+6-9-1+8+4)^{34} \\ & := (1-7+17+9+8-6-9+1-8-4)^{34} & := (-1+7-17+9-8-6+9-1+8+4)^{17} \\ & := (-1-7+17+9-8-6+9+1-8-4)^{34} & := (-1+7-17-9+8-6+9-1+8+4)^{34} \\ & := (1-7+17+9-8-6+9+1-8-4)^{17} & := (1+7-17-9+8-6+9-1+8+4)^{17} \\ & := (1-7+17-9+8-6+9+1-8-4)^{34} & := (-1-7-17+9-8+6+9-1+8+4)^{34} \\ & := (1-7+17+9-8-6-9+1+8-4)^{34} & := (1-7-17+9-8+6+9-1+8+4)^{17} \\ & := (1-7+17-9-8-6+9+1+8-4)^{34} & := (1-7-17-9+8+6+9-1+8+4)^{34} \\ & := (1-7-17+9+8-6+9+1+8-4)^{34} & := (-1+7+17-9-8-6-9+1+8+4)^{17} \\ & := (-1+7+17+9-8-6-9-1-8+4)^{17} & := (-1+7-17+9+8-6-9+1+8+4)^{17} \\ & := (-1+7+17-9+8-6-9-1-8+4)^{34} & := (-1-7+17-9-8+6-9+1+8+4)^{34} \\ & := (1+7+17-9+8-6-9-1-8+4)^{17} & := (1-7+17-9-8+6-9+1+8+4)^{17} \\ & := (-1-7+17+9-8+6-9-1-8+4)^{34} & := (1+7-17+9-8+6-9+1+8+4)^{34} \\ & := (1-7+17+9-8+6-9-1-8+4)^{17} & := (-1-7-17+9+8+6-9+1+8+4)^{34} \\ & := (1-7+17-9+8+6-9-1-8+4)^{34} & := (1-7-17+9+8+6-9+1+8+4)^{17} \\ & := (-1+7+17-9-8-6+9-1-8+4)^{17} & := (-1+7-17-9+8-6+9+1+8+4)^{17} \\ & := (-1+7-17+9+8-6+9-1-8+4)^{17} & := (1+7-17-9-8+6+9+1+8+4)^{34} \\ & := (-1-7+17-9-8+6+9-1-8+4)^{34} & := (-1-7-17+9-8+6+9+1+8+4)^{17} \\ & := (1-7+17-9-8+6+9-1-8+4)^{17} & := (-1-7-17-9+8+6+9+1+8+4)^{34} \\ & := (1+7-17+9-8+6+9-1-8+4)^{34} & := (1-7-17-9+8+6+9+1+8+4)^{17} \\ & := (-1-7-17+9+8+6+9-1-8+4)^{34} & := (-1+7-1+7+9+8+6-9-18-4)^{17} \\ & := (1-7-17+9+8+6+9-1-8+4)^{17} & := (-1+7-1+7-9+8+6+9-18-4)^{17} \\ & := (-1+7+17-9+8-6-9+1-8+4)^{17} & := (1+7+1-7+9-8-6-9+18-4)^{34} \\ & := (1+7+17-9-8+6-9+1-8+4)^{34} & := (1-7+1+7+9-8-6-9+18-4)^{34} \\ & := (-1-7+17+9-8+6-9+1-8+4)^{17} & := (1-7-1-7+9+8-6-9+18-4)^{34} \\ & := (-1-7+17-9+8+6-9+1-8+4)^{34} & := (-1-7+1-7+9+8-6-9+18-4)^{34} \\ & := (1-7+17-9+8+6-9+1-8+4)^{17} & := (1-7+1-7+9+8-6-9+18-4)^{17} \\ & := (1+7-17+9+8+6-9+1-8+4)^{34} & := (1+7+1-7-9-8-6+9+18-4)^{34} \\ & := (-1-7+17-9-8+6+9+1-8+4)^{17} & := (1-7+1+7-9-8-6+9+18-4)^{34} \\ & := (-1+7-17+9-8+6+9+1-8+4)^{34} & := (-1-7-1-7+9-8-6+9+18-4)^{34} \\ & := (1+7-17+9-8+6+9+1-8+4)^{17} & := (1-7-1-7+9-8-6+9+18-4)^{17} \\ & := (1+7-17-9+8+6+9+1-8+4)^{34} & := (-1-7+1-7+9-8-6+9+18-4)^{17} \\ & := (-1-7-17+9+8+6+9+1-8+4)^{17} & := (1-7-1-7-9+8-6+9+18-4)^{34} \\ & := (-1+7+17-9-8-6-9-1+8+4)^{34} & := (-1-7+1-7-9+8-6+9+18-4)^{34} \\ & := (1+7+17-9-8-6-9-1+8+4)^{17} & := (1-7+1-7-9+8-6+9+18-4)^{17} \\ & := (-1-7+17-9+8-6-9-1+8+4)^{17} & := (1+7-1+7+9+8-6-9-18+4)^{34} \\ & := (-1+7-17+9+8-6-9-1+8+4)^{34} & := (-1+7+1+7+9+8-6-9-18+4)^{34} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} & := (1+7+1+7+9+8-6-9-18+4)^{17} & := (1+71-7+9-86+9+1+8-4)^{34} \\ & := (1+7+1-7+9+8+6-9-18+4)^{34} & := (-1-71-7+9+86-9-1-8+4)^{34} \\ & := (1-7+1+7+9+8+6-9-18+4)^{34} & := (1-71-7+9+86-9-1-8+4)^{17} \\ & := (-1+7-1+7+9-8-6+9-18+4)^{34} & := (-1+71+7+9-86+9-1-8+4)^{17} \\ & := (1+7-1+7+9-8-6+9-18+4)^{17} & := (-1-71-7-9+86+9-1-8+4)^{34} \\ & := (-1+7+1+7+9-8-6+9-18+4)^{17} & := (1-71-7-9+86+9-1-8+4)^{17} \\ & := (1+7-1+7-9+8-6+9-18+4)^{34} & := (1-71+7-9+86-9+1-8+4)^{34} \\ & := (-1+7+1+7-9+8-6+9-18+4)^{34} & := (-1-71-7+9+86-9+1-8+4)^{17} \\ & := (1+7+1+7-9+8-6+9-18+4)^{17} & := (-1-71-7-9+86+9+1-8+4)^{17} \\ & := (-1+7-1-7+9+8-6+9-18+4)^{17} & := (-1+71+7+9-86-9-1+8+4)^{34} \\ & := (-1-7-1+7+9+8-6+9-18+4)^{17} & := (1+71+7+9-86-9-1+8+4)^{17} \\ & := (1+7-1-7+9-8+6+9-18+4)^{34} & := (1-71-7-9+86-9-1+8+4)^{34} \\ & := (-1+7+1-7+9-8+6+9-18+4)^{34} & := (-1+71+7-9-86+9-1+8+4)^{34} \\ & := (1+7+1-7+9-8+6+9-18+4)^{17} & := (1+71+7-9-86+9-1+8+4)^{17} \\ & := (1-7-1+7+9-8+6+9-18+4)^{34} & := (-1+71+7+9-86-9+1+8+4)^{17} \\ & := (-1-7+1+7+9-8+6+9-18+4)^{34} & := (-1-71-7-9+86-9+1+8+4)^{34} \\ & := (1-7+1+7+9-8+6+9-18+4)^{17} & := (1-71-7-9+86-9+1+8+4)^{17} \\ & := (1+7+1-7-9+8+6+9-18+4)^{34} & := (-1+71+7-9-86+9+1+8+4)^{17} \\ & := (1-7+1+7-9+8+6+9-18+4)^{34} & := (1+71-7+9+8-69+1-8-4)^{34} \\ & := (-1-7-1-7+9+8+6+9-18+4)^{34} & := (1+71-7+9-8-69+1+8-4)^{34} \\ & := (1-7-1-7+9+8+6+9-18+4)^{17} & := (-1+71+7+9-8-69-1-8+4)^{17} \\ & := (-1-7+1-7+9+8+6+9-18+4)^{17} & := (-1+71+7-9+8-69-1-8+4)^{34} \\ & := (-1+7-1+7-9-8-6-9+18+4)^{34} & := (1+71+7-9+8-69-1-8+4)^{17} \\ & := (1+7-1+7-9-8-6-9+18+4)^{17} & := (1-71+7+9-8+69-1-8+4)^{34} \\ & := (-1+7+1+7-9-8-6-9+18+4)^{17} & := (-1-71-7+9+8+69-1-8+4)^{34} \\ & := (-1+7-1-7-9+8-6-9+18+4)^{17} & := (1-71-7+9+8+69-1-8+4)^{17} \\ & := (-1-7-1+7-9+8-6-9+18+4)^{17} & := (-1+71+7-9+8-69+1-8+4)^{17} \\ & := (1+7-1-7-9-8+6-9+18+4)^{34} & := (-1-71+7+9-8+69+1-8+4)^{34} \\ & := (-1+7+1-7-9-8+6-9+18+4)^{34} & := (1-71+7+9-8+69+1-8+4)^{17} \\ & := (1+7+1-7-9-8+6-9+18+4)^{17} & := (1-71+7-9+8+69+1-8+4)^{34} \\ & := (1-7-1+7-9-8+6-9+18+4)^{34} & := (-1-71-7+9+8+69+1-8+4)^{17} \\ & := (-1-7+1+7-9-8+6-9+18+4)^{34} & := (-1+71+7-9-8-69-1+8+4)^{34} \\ & := (1-7+1+7-9-8+6-9+18+4)^{17} & := (1+71+7-9-8-69-1+8+4)^{17} \\ & := (-1-7-1-7+9-8+6-9+18+4)^{17} & := (-1+71-7-9+8-69-1+8+4)^{17} \\ & := (-1-7-1-7-9+8+6-9+18+4)^{34} & := (-1-71-7+9-8+69-1+8+4)^{34} \\ & := (1-7-1-7-9+8+6-9+18+4)^{17} & := (1-71-7+9-8+69-1+8+4)^{17} \\ & := (-1-7+1-7-9+8+6-9+18+4)^{17} & := (1-71-7-9+8+69-1+8+4)^{34} \\ & := (-1-7-1-7-9+8+6-9+18+4)^{17} & := (-1+71+7-9-8-69+1+8+4)^{17} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} &:= (1 - 71 + 7 - 9 - 8 + 69 + 1 + 8 + 4)^{34} &:= (1 - 7 + 1 - 79 + 86 - 9 - 1 + 8 + 4)^{17} \\ &:= (-1 - 71 - 7 + 9 - 8 + 69 + 1 + 8 + 4)^{17} &:= (-1 - 7 - 1 + 79 - 86 + 9 - 1 + 8 + 4)^{17} \\ &:= (-1 - 71 - 7 - 9 + 8 + 69 + 1 + 8 + 4)^{34} &:= (-1 + 7 - 1 + 79 - 86 - 9 + 1 + 8 + 4)^{34} \\ &:= (1 - 71 - 7 - 9 + 8 + 69 + 1 + 8 + 4)^{17} &:= (1 + 7 - 1 + 79 - 86 - 9 + 1 + 8 + 4)^{17} \\ &:= (1 + 71 - 7 + 9 + 8 - 6 + 9 + 1 - 84)^{34} &:= (-1 + 7 + 1 + 79 - 86 - 9 + 1 + 8 + 4)^{17} \\ &:= (-1 - 71 + 7 + 9 - 8 - 6 - 9 - 1 + 84)^{17} &:= (-1 - 7 - 1 - 79 + 86 - 9 + 1 + 8 + 4)^{34} \\ &:= (-1 - 71 + 7 - 9 + 8 - 6 - 9 - 1 + 84)^{34} &:= (1 - 7 - 1 - 79 + 86 - 9 + 1 + 8 + 4)^{17} \\ &:= (1 - 71 + 7 - 9 + 8 - 6 - 9 - 1 + 84)^{17} &:= (-1 - 7 + 1 - 79 + 86 - 9 + 1 + 8 + 4)^{17} \\ &:= (-1 - 71 - 7 + 9 - 8 + 6 - 9 - 1 + 84)^{34} &:= (1 - 7 + 1 + 79 + 8 - 69 + 1 - 8 - 4)^{34} \\ &:= (1 - 71 - 7 + 9 - 8 + 6 - 9 - 1 + 84)^{17} &:= (1 - 7 + 1 + 79 - 8 - 69 + 1 + 8 - 4)^{34} \\ &:= (1 - 71 - 7 - 9 + 8 + 6 - 9 - 1 + 84)^{34} &:= (-1 + 7 - 1 + 79 - 8 - 69 - 1 - 8 + 4)^{34} \\ &:= (-1 - 71 + 7 - 9 - 8 - 6 + 9 - 1 + 84)^{17} &:= (1 + 7 - 1 + 79 - 8 - 69 - 1 - 8 + 4)^{17} \\ &:= (-1 - 71 - 7 - 9 - 8 + 6 + 9 - 1 + 84)^{34} &:= (-1 + 7 + 1 + 79 - 8 - 69 - 1 - 8 + 4)^{17} \\ &:= (1 - 71 - 7 - 9 - 8 + 6 + 9 - 1 + 84)^{17} &:= (-1 - 7 - 1 + 79 + 8 - 69 - 1 - 8 + 4)^{17} \\ &:= (-1 - 71 + 7 - 9 + 8 - 6 - 9 + 1 + 84)^{17} &:= (1 + 7 + 1 - 79 + 8 + 69 - 1 - 8 + 4)^{34} \\ &:= (1 - 71 + 7 - 9 - 8 + 6 - 9 + 1 + 84)^{34} &:= (-1 + 7 - 1 + 79 - 8 - 69 + 1 - 8 + 4)^{17} \\ &:= (-1 - 71 - 7 + 9 - 8 + 6 - 9 + 1 + 84)^{17} &:= (1 + 7 - 1 - 79 + 8 + 69 + 1 - 8 + 4)^{34} \\ &:= (-1 - 71 - 7 - 9 + 8 + 6 - 9 + 1 + 84)^{34} &:= (-1 + 7 + 1 - 79 + 8 + 69 + 1 - 8 + 4)^{34} \\ &:= (1 - 71 - 7 - 9 + 8 + 6 - 9 + 1 + 84)^{17} &:= (1 + 7 + 1 - 79 + 8 + 69 + 1 - 8 + 4)^{17} \\ &:= (-1 - 71 - 7 - 9 - 8 + 6 + 9 + 1 + 84)^{17} &:= (-1 - 7 - 1 + 79 - 8 - 69 - 1 + 8 + 4)^{17} \\ &:= (1 - 7 + 1 + 79 - 86 + 9 + 1 + 8 - 4)^{34} &:= (1 + 7 + 1 - 79 - 8 + 69 - 1 + 8 + 4)^{34} \\ &:= (1 + 7 + 1 - 79 + 86 - 9 - 1 - 8 + 4)^{34} &:= (1 - 7 - 1 - 79 + 8 + 69 - 1 + 8 + 4)^{34} \\ &:= (-1 + 7 - 1 + 79 - 86 + 9 - 1 - 8 + 4)^{34} &:= (-1 - 7 + 1 - 79 + 8 + 69 - 1 + 8 + 4)^{34} \\ &:= (1 + 7 - 1 + 79 - 86 + 9 - 1 - 8 + 4)^{17} &:= (1 - 7 + 1 - 79 + 8 + 69 - 1 + 8 + 4)^{17} \\ &:= (-1 + 7 + 1 + 79 - 86 + 9 - 1 - 8 + 4)^{17} &:= (1 + 7 - 1 - 79 - 8 + 69 + 1 + 8 + 4)^{34} \\ &:= (-1 - 7 - 1 - 79 + 86 + 9 - 1 - 8 + 4)^{34} &:= (-1 + 7 + 1 - 79 - 8 + 69 + 1 + 8 + 4)^{34} \\ &:= (1 - 7 - 1 - 79 + 86 + 9 - 1 - 8 + 4)^{17} &:= (1 + 7 + 1 - 79 - 8 + 69 + 1 + 8 + 4)^{17} \\ &:= (-1 - 7 + 1 - 79 + 86 + 9 - 1 - 8 + 4)^{17} &:= (-1 - 7 - 1 - 79 + 8 + 69 + 1 + 8 + 4)^{34} \\ &:= (1 + 7 - 1 - 79 + 86 - 9 + 1 - 8 + 4)^{34} &:= (1 - 7 - 1 - 79 + 8 + 69 + 1 + 8 + 4)^{17} \\ &:= (-1 + 7 + 1 - 79 + 86 - 9 + 1 - 8 + 4)^{34} &:= (-1 - 7 + 1 - 79 + 8 + 69 + 1 + 8 + 4)^{17} \\ &:= (1 + 7 + 1 - 79 + 86 - 9 + 1 - 8 + 4)^{17} &:= (-1 + 7 - 1 + 79 + 8 + 6 - 9 - 1 - 84)^{17} \\ &:= (-1 + 7 - 1 + 79 - 86 + 9 + 1 - 8 + 4)^{17} &:= (1 - 7 + 1 + 79 + 8 - 6 + 9 + 1 - 84)^{34} \\ &:= (-1 - 7 - 1 - 79 + 86 + 9 + 1 - 8 + 4)^{17} &:= (-1 + 7 - 1 - 79 + 8 - 6 - 9 - 1 + 84)^{34} \\ &:= (1 + 7 - 1 + 79 - 86 - 9 - 1 + 8 + 4)^{34} &:= (1 + 7 - 1 - 79 + 8 - 6 - 9 - 1 + 84)^{17} \\ &:= (-1 + 7 + 1 + 79 - 86 - 9 - 1 + 8 + 4)^{34} &:= (-1 + 7 + 1 - 79 + 8 - 6 - 9 - 1 + 84)^{17} \\ &:= (1 + 7 + 1 + 79 - 86 - 9 - 1 + 8 + 4)^{17} &:= (1 + 7 + 1 - 79 - 8 + 6 - 9 - 1 + 84)^{34} \\ &:= (1 - 7 - 1 - 79 + 86 - 9 - 1 + 8 + 4)^{34} &:= (1 - 7 - 1 - 79 + 8 + 6 - 9 - 1 + 84)^{34} \\ &:= (-1 - 7 + 1 - 79 + 86 - 9 - 1 + 8 + 4)^{34} &:= (-1 - 7 + 1 - 79 + 8 + 6 - 9 - 1 + 84)^{34} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} & := (1 - 7 + 1 - 79 + 8 + 6 - 9 - 1 + 84)^{17} & := (1 - 7 - 1 + 7 - 98 + 6 + 9 + 1 + 84)^{34} \\ & := (-1 + 7 - 1 - 79 - 8 - 6 + 9 - 1 + 84)^{17} & := (-1 - 7 + 1 + 7 - 98 + 6 + 9 + 1 + 84)^{34} \\ & := (-1 - 7 - 1 - 79 - 8 + 6 + 9 - 1 + 84)^{34} & := (1 - 7 + 1 + 7 - 98 + 6 + 9 + 1 + 84)^{17} \\ & := (1 - 7 - 1 - 79 - 8 + 6 + 9 - 1 + 84)^{17} & := (-1 + 7 - 1 + 7 + 9 + 86 - 91 - 8 - 4)^{17} \\ & := (-1 - 7 + 1 - 79 - 8 + 6 + 9 - 1 + 84)^{17} & := (1 + 7 - 1 - 7 + 9 - 86 + 91 - 8 - 4)^{34} \\ & := (-1 + 7 - 1 - 79 + 8 - 6 - 9 + 1 + 84)^{17} & := (-1 + 7 + 1 - 7 + 9 - 86 + 91 - 8 - 4)^{34} \\ & := (1 + 7 - 1 - 79 - 8 + 6 - 9 + 1 + 84)^{34} & := (1 + 7 + 1 - 7 + 9 - 86 + 91 - 8 - 4)^{17} \\ & := (-1 + 7 + 1 - 79 - 8 + 6 - 9 + 1 + 84)^{34} & := (1 - 7 - 1 + 7 + 9 - 86 + 91 - 8 - 4)^{34} \\ & := (1 + 7 + 1 - 79 - 8 + 6 - 9 + 1 + 84)^{17} & := (-1 - 7 + 1 + 7 + 9 - 86 + 91 - 8 - 4)^{34} \\ & := (-1 - 7 - 1 - 79 + 8 + 6 - 9 + 1 + 84)^{34} & := (1 - 7 + 1 + 7 + 9 - 86 + 91 - 8 - 4)^{17} \\ & := (1 - 7 - 1 - 79 + 8 + 6 - 9 + 1 + 84)^{17} & := (-1 + 7 - 1 + 7 - 9 + 86 - 91 + 8 - 4)^{34} \\ & := (-1 - 7 + 1 - 79 + 8 + 6 - 9 + 1 + 84)^{17} & := (1 + 7 - 1 + 7 - 9 + 86 - 91 + 8 - 4)^{17} \\ & := (-1 - 7 - 1 - 79 - 8 + 6 + 9 + 1 + 84)^{17} & := (-1 + 7 + 1 + 7 - 9 + 86 - 91 + 8 - 4)^{17} \\ & := (1 - 7 - 1 - 7 + 98 - 69 - 1 - 8 - 4)^{34} & := (1 + 7 + 1 - 7 - 9 - 86 + 91 + 8 - 4)^{34} \\ & := (-1 - 7 + 1 - 7 + 98 - 69 - 1 - 8 - 4)^{34} & := (1 - 7 + 1 + 7 - 9 - 86 + 91 + 8 - 4)^{34} \\ & := (1 - 7 + 1 - 7 + 98 - 69 - 1 - 8 - 4)^{17} & := (-1 - 7 - 1 - 7 + 9 - 86 + 91 + 8 - 4)^{34} \\ & := (-1 - 7 - 1 - 7 + 98 - 69 + 1 - 8 - 4)^{34} & := (1 - 7 - 1 - 7 + 9 - 86 + 91 + 8 - 4)^{17} \\ & := (1 - 7 - 1 - 7 + 98 - 69 + 1 - 8 - 4)^{17} & := (-1 - 7 + 1 - 7 + 9 - 86 + 91 + 8 - 4)^{17} \\ & := (-1 - 7 + 1 - 7 + 98 - 69 + 1 - 8 - 4)^{17} & := (1 + 7 + 1 - 7 + 9 + 86 - 91 - 8 + 4)^{34} \\ & := (1 - 7 - 1 - 7 + 98 - 6 + 9 - 1 - 84)^{34} & := (1 - 7 + 1 + 7 + 9 + 86 - 91 - 8 + 4)^{34} \\ & := (-1 - 7 + 1 - 7 + 98 - 6 + 9 - 1 - 84)^{34} & := (-1 + 7 - 1 + 7 - 9 - 86 + 91 - 8 + 4)^{17} \\ & := (1 - 7 + 1 - 7 + 98 - 6 + 9 - 1 - 84)^{17} & := (1 - 7 - 1 - 7 + 9 + 86 - 91 + 8 + 4)^{34} \\ & := (1 + 7 + 1 - 7 + 98 - 6 - 9 + 1 - 84)^{34} & := (-1 - 7 + 1 - 7 + 9 + 86 - 91 + 8 + 4)^{34} \\ & := (1 - 7 + 1 + 7 + 98 - 6 - 9 + 1 - 84)^{34} & := (1 - 7 + 1 - 7 + 9 + 86 - 91 + 8 + 4)^{17} \\ & := (-1 - 7 - 1 - 7 + 98 - 6 + 9 + 1 - 84)^{34} & := (1 + 7 - 1 - 7 + 9 - 8 - 6 + 91 - 84)^{34} \\ & := (1 - 7 - 1 - 7 + 98 - 6 + 9 + 1 - 84)^{17} & := (-1 + 7 + 1 - 7 + 9 - 8 - 6 + 91 - 84)^{34} \\ & := (-1 - 7 + 1 - 7 + 98 - 6 + 9 + 1 - 84)^{17} & := (1 + 7 + 1 - 7 + 9 - 8 - 6 + 91 - 84)^{17} \\ & := (1 + 7 - 1 + 7 - 98 - 6 + 9 - 1 + 84)^{34} & := (1 - 7 - 1 + 7 + 9 - 8 - 6 + 91 - 84)^{34} \\ & := (-1 + 7 + 1 + 7 - 98 - 6 + 9 - 1 + 84)^{34} & := (-1 - 7 + 1 + 7 + 9 - 8 - 6 + 91 - 84)^{34} \\ & := (1 + 7 + 1 + 7 - 98 - 6 + 9 - 1 + 84)^{17} & := (1 - 7 + 1 + 7 + 9 - 8 - 6 + 91 - 84)^{17} \\ & := (1 + 7 + 1 - 7 - 98 + 6 + 9 - 1 + 84)^{34} & := (1 + 7 + 1 - 7 - 9 + 8 - 6 + 91 - 84)^{34} \\ & := (1 - 7 + 1 + 7 - 98 + 6 + 9 - 1 + 84)^{34} & := (1 - 7 + 1 + 7 - 9 + 8 - 6 + 91 - 84)^{34} \\ & := (-1 + 7 - 1 + 7 - 98 - 6 + 9 + 1 + 84)^{34} & := (-1 - 7 - 1 - 7 + 9 + 8 - 6 + 91 - 84)^{34} \\ & := (1 + 7 - 1 + 7 - 98 - 6 + 9 + 1 + 84)^{17} & := (1 - 7 - 1 - 7 + 9 + 8 - 6 + 91 - 84)^{17} \\ & := (-1 + 7 + 1 + 7 - 98 - 6 + 9 + 1 + 84)^{17} & := (-1 - 7 + 1 - 7 + 9 + 8 - 6 + 91 - 84)^{17} \\ & := (1 + 7 - 1 - 7 - 98 + 6 + 9 + 1 + 84)^{34} & := (1 - 7 + 1 - 7 + 9 - 8 + 6 + 91 - 84)^{34} \\ & := (-1 + 7 + 1 - 7 - 98 + 6 + 9 + 1 + 84)^{34} & := (1 + 7 - 1 + 7 + 9 - 8 - 6 - 91 + 84)^{34} \\ & := (1 + 7 + 1 - 7 - 98 + 6 + 9 + 1 + 84)^{17} & := (-1 + 7 + 1 + 7 + 9 - 8 - 6 - 91 + 84)^{34} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} &:= (1+7+1+7+9-8-6-91+84)^{17} & &:= (-17-1+7+9-86+9-1+84)^{17} \\ &:= (1+7+1+7-9+8-6-91+84)^{34} & &:= (17-1+7-9-86-9+1+84)^{17} \\ &:= (-1+7-1-7+9+8-6-91+84)^{34} & &:= (-17-1+7+9-8-69-1+84)^{17} \\ &:= (1+7-1-7+9+8-6-91+84)^{17} & &:= (-17-1+7-9+8-69-1+84)^{34} \\ &:= (-1+7+1-7+9+8-6-91+84)^{17} & &:= (-17+1+7-9+8-69-1+84)^{17} \\ &:= (-1-7-1+7+9+8-6-91+84)^{34} & &:= (-17-1+7-9+8-69+1+84)^{17} \\ &:= (1-7-1+7+9+8-6-91+84)^{17} & &:= (1+71-79-8-6+9+18-4)^{34} \\ &:= (-1-7+1+7+9+8-6-91+84)^{17} & &:= (-1-71+79+8-6+9-18+4)^{17} \\ &:= (1+7+1-7+9-8+6-91+84)^{34} & &:= (1-71+79-8+6+9-18+4)^{34} \\ &:= (1-7+1+7+9-8+6-91+84)^{34} & &:= (1+71-79+8+6+9-18+4)^{34} \\ &:= (1-7-1-7+9+8+6-91+84)^{34} & &:= (-1+71-79-8+6-9+18+4)^{34} \\ &:= (-1-7+1-7+9+8+6-91+84)^{34} & &:= (1+71-79-8+6-9+18+4)^{17} \\ &:= (1-7+1-7+9+8+6-91+84)^{17} & &:= (1-71-7+98-6+9-18-4)^{34} \\ &:= (17+17-9+8-6-9-18+4)^{17} & &:= (-1-71+7+98-6-9-18+4)^{17} \\ &:= (17-17+9-8+6+9-18+4)^{34} & &:= (-1-71-7+98+6-9-18+4)^{34} \\ &:= (-17+17+9-8+6+9-18+4)^{34} & &:= (1-71-7+98+6-9-18+4)^{17} \\ &:= (17-17-9-8+6-9+18+4)^{34} & &:= (-1+71+7-98-6+9+18+4)^{17} \\ &:= (-17+17-9-8+6-9+18+4)^{34} & &:= (-1+71-7-98+6+9+18+4)^{34} \\ &:= (-17-17+9+8+6-9+18+4)^{34} & &:= (1+71-7-98+6+9+18+4)^{17} \\ &:= (-17-17+9-8+6+9+18+4)^{17} & &:= (1-7+17-98-6+91+8-4)^{34} \\ &:= (-17-17-9+8+6+9+18+4)^{34} & &:= (-1-7+17-98+6+91-8+4)^{17} \\ &:= (17-1-79-8-6+91-8-4)^{34} & &:= (-1+7-17+98-6-91+8+4)^{34} \\ &:= (17+1-79-8-6+91-8-4)^{17} & &:= (1+7-17+98-6-91+8+4)^{17} \\ &:= (-17+1-79+8-6+91+8-4)^{34} & &:= (1-7-17+98+6-91+8+4)^{34} \\ &:= (17-1+79+8-6-91-8+4)^{34} & &:= (1+7-17-98+6+91+8+4)^{34} \\ &:= (17+1+79+8-6-91-8+4)^{17} & &:= (-1+7+17-9-86-9-1+84)^{34} \\ &:= (-17-1-79+8+6+91-8+4)^{17} & &:= (1+7+17-9-86-9-1+84)^{17} \\ &:= (17-1+79-8-6-91+8+4)^{34} & &:= (-1+7-17+9-86+9-1+84)^{17} \\ &:= (17+1+79-8-6-91+8+4)^{17} & &:= (-1+7+17-9-86-9+1+84)^{17} \\ &:= (-17-1-79-8+6+91+8+4)^{17} & &:= (-1+7-17+9-8-69-1+84)^{17} \\ &:= (17+1-7-98-6+91+8-4)^{34} & &:= (-1+7-17-9+8-69-1+84)^{34} \\ &:= (17-1-7-98+6+91-8+4)^{17} & &:= (1+7-17-9+8-69-1+84)^{17} \\ &:= (-17-1+7+98-6-91+8+4)^{34} & &:= (-1+7-17-9+8-69+1+84)^{17} \\ &:= (-17+1+7+98-6-91+8+4)^{17} & &:= (171-79-86+9-1-8-4)^{34} \\ &:= (-17+1-7+98+6-91+8+4)^{34} & &:= (171-79-86+9+1-8-4)^{17} \\ &:= (-17+1+7-98+6+91+8+4)^{34} & &:= (171-79-86-9+1+8-4)^{34} \\ &:= (17-1+7-9-86-9-1+84)^{34} & &:= (171-79-8-69-1-8-4)^{34} \\ &:= (17+1+7-9-86-9-1+84)^{17} & &:= (171-79-8-69+1-8-4)^{17} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 &:= (171 - 79 - 8 - 6 + 9 - 1 - 84)^{34} & &:= (17 + 1 - 79 + 8 + 69 - 18 + 4)^{34} \\
 &:= (171 - 79 + 8 - 6 - 9 + 1 - 84)^{34} & &:= (-17 - 1 - 79 + 8 + 69 + 18 + 4)^{34} \\
 &:= (171 - 79 - 8 - 6 + 9 + 1 - 84)^{17} & &:= (-17 + 1 - 79 + 8 + 69 + 18 + 4)^{17} \\
 &:= (-171 + 79 + 8 - 6 + 9 - 1 + 84)^{34} & &:= (-17 - 1 + 7 + 98 - 69 - 18 + 4)^{17} \\
 &:= (-171 + 79 + 8 - 6 + 9 + 1 + 84)^{17} & &:= (17 - 1 - 7 - 98 + 69 + 18 + 4)^{34} \\
 &:= (171 - 7 - 98 - 69 + 1 + 8 - 4)^{34} & &:= (17 + 1 - 7 - 98 + 69 + 18 + 4)^{17} \\
 &:= (-171 - 7 + 98 + 69 + 1 + 8 + 4)^{34} & &:= (-1 + 717 - 9 - 8 - 691 - 8 + 4)^{17} \\
 &:= (-171 + 7 + 98 - 6 - 9 - 1 + 84)^{34} & &:= (-1 - 717 + 9 + 8 + 691 + 8 + 4)^{34} \\
 &:= (-171 + 7 + 98 - 6 - 9 + 1 + 84)^{17} & &:= (1 - 717 + 9 + 8 + 691 + 8 + 4)^{17} \\
 &:= (-171 - 7 + 98 + 6 - 9 + 1 + 84)^{34} & &:= (1 - 71 + 79 - 86 + 91 - 8 - 4)^{34} \\
 &:= (-171 - 7 + 9 + 86 + 91 - 8 + 4)^{17} & &:= (1 + 71 - 79 - 86 + 91 + 8 - 4)^{34} \\
 &:= (171 + 7 - 9 - 86 - 91 + 8 + 4)^{17} & &:= (1 - 71 + 79 - 8 - 6 + 91 - 84)^{34} \\
 &:= (-171 - 7 - 9 + 86 + 91 + 8 + 4)^{34} & &:= (1 + 71 - 79 + 8 - 6 + 91 - 84)^{34} \\
 &:= (-171 + 7 - 9 + 8 - 6 + 91 + 84)^{17} & &:= (-1 - 71 + 79 + 8 - 6 - 91 + 84)^{34} \\
 &:= (-171 - 7 + 9 - 8 + 6 + 91 + 84)^{17} & &:= (1 - 71 + 79 + 8 - 6 - 91 + 84)^{17} \\
 &:= (-171 - 7 - 9 + 8 + 6 + 91 + 84)^{34} & &:= (-1 - 71 - 7 - 98 + 6 + 91 + 84)^{17} \\
 &:= (-171 + 7 - 9 + 8 - 6 - 9 + 184)^{17} & &:= (-1 - 71 - 7 - 98 + 6 - 9 + 184)^{17} \\
 &:= (-171 - 7 + 9 - 8 + 6 - 9 + 184)^{17} & &:= (-1 + 7 + 179 - 86 - 91 - 8 + 4)^{17} \\
 &:= (-171 - 7 - 9 + 8 + 6 - 9 + 184)^{34} & &:= (1 + 7 - 179 + 86 + 91 - 8 + 4)^{34} \\
 &:= (-171 - 7 - 9 - 8 + 6 + 9 + 184)^{17} & &:= (-1 - 7 - 179 + 86 + 91 + 8 + 4)^{34} \\
 &:= (17 + 17 - 98 + 69 + 1 - 8 + 4)^{34} & &:= (1 - 7 - 179 + 86 + 91 + 8 + 4)^{17} \\
 &:= (17 + 17 - 98 - 6 - 9 - 1 + 84)^{17} & &:= (-1 + 7 - 179 + 8 - 6 + 91 + 84)^{17} \\
 &:= (17 - 17 - 98 + 6 + 9 + 1 + 84)^{34} & &:= (1 + 7 - 179 - 8 + 6 + 91 + 84)^{34} \\
 &:= (-17 + 17 - 98 + 6 + 9 + 1 + 84)^{34} & &:= (-1 - 7 - 179 + 8 + 6 + 91 + 84)^{34} \\
 &:= (17 - 17 + 9 - 86 + 91 - 8 - 4)^{34} & &:= (1 - 7 - 179 + 8 + 6 + 91 + 84)^{17} \\
 &:= (-17 + 17 + 9 - 86 + 91 - 8 - 4)^{34} & &:= (-1 + 7 - 179 + 8 - 6 - 9 + 184)^{17} \\
 &:= (-17 - 17 - 9 - 8 + 69 - 18 + 4)^{17} & &:= (1 + 7 - 179 - 8 + 6 - 9 + 184)^{34} \\
 &:= (17 + 17 + 9 + 8 - 69 + 18 + 4)^{17} & &:= (-1 - 7 - 179 + 8 + 6 - 9 + 184)^{34} \\
 &:= (17 - 17 + 9 - 8 - 6 + 91 - 84)^{34} & &:= (1 - 7 - 179 + 8 + 6 - 9 + 184)^{17} \\
 &:= (-17 + 17 + 9 - 8 - 6 + 91 - 84)^{34} & &:= (-1 - 7 - 179 - 8 + 6 + 9 + 184)^{17} \\
 &:= (17 + 17 - 9 - 8 - 6 - 91 + 84)^{17} & &:= (-1 + 7 - 17 + 98 - 69 - 18 + 4)^{17} \\
 &:= (17 - 17 + 9 + 8 - 6 - 91 + 84)^{17} & &:= (-1 - 7 + 17 - 98 + 69 + 18 + 4)^{34} \\
 &:= (-17 + 17 + 9 + 8 - 6 - 91 + 84)^{17} & &:= (1 - 7 + 17 - 98 + 69 + 18 + 4)^{17} \\
 &:= (17 + 1 - 79 + 86 - 9 - 18 + 4)^{34} & &:= (-17 + 179 - 86 + 9 + 1 - 84)^{34} \\
 &:= (17 - 1 + 79 - 86 + 9 - 18 + 4)^{17} & &:= (-17 + 179 - 8 - 69 + 1 - 84)^{34} \\
 &:= (-17 - 1 - 79 + 86 - 9 + 18 + 4)^{34} & &:= (17 - 1 + 79 - 86 - 91 + 84)^{34} \\
 &:= (-17 + 1 - 79 + 86 - 9 + 18 + 4)^{17} & &:= (17 + 1 + 79 - 86 - 91 + 84)^{17} \\
 &:= (17 - 1 + 79 - 8 - 69 - 18 + 4)^{17} & &
 \end{aligned}$$

17213481368 := (1721 + 34 + 813 + 6 + 8)³

$$\begin{aligned} 17249876309 &:= (17+2+4+9+8+7-6-3-09)^7 & := (-17+2-4+9-8-7+63-09)^7 \\ &:= (17-2-4+9+8+7+6-3-09)^7 & := (-17-2+4-9-8+7+63-09)^7 \\ &:= (17-2+4+9+8-7+6+3-09)^7 & := (-17+2-4-9-8-7+63+09)^7 \\ &:= (17+2+4-9+8+7+6+3-09)^7 & := (-1+72-49+8-7-6+3+09)^7 \\ &:= (17-2+4+9+8-7-6-3+09)^7 & := (1+72-49-8+7-6+3+09)^7 \\ &:= (17+2+4-9+8+7-6-3+09)^7 & := (1-72+4+9+87+6+3-09)^7 \\ &:= (17+2+4+9-8-7+6-3+09)^7 & := (1-72+4+9+87-6-3+09)^7 \\ &:= (17-2-4-9+8+7+6-3+09)^7 & := (1-72+4-9+87+6+3+09)^7 \\ &:= (17+2-4+9-8+7-6+3+09)^7 & := (1+72+4+9+8+7-63-09)^7 \\ &:= (17-2+4-9+8-7+6+3+09)^7 & := (-1+72+4+9-8+7-63+09)^7 \\ &:= (-1+7+2-4+9+8-7-6+30-9)^7 & := (1+72+4-9+8+7-63+09)^7 \\ &:= (1+7+2-4+9-8+7-6+30-9)^7 & := (1-72+4+9+8+7+63+09)^7 \\ &:= (-1+7-2+4-9+8+7-6+30-9)^7 & := (-1+7-24-9-8+76-3-09)^7 \\ &:= (-1-7+2-4+9+8+7-6+30-9)^7 & := (1+7+24+9+8+7-6-30+9)^7 \\ &:= (-1+7-2+4+9-8-7+6+30-9)^7 & := (1+7-2-49+8+76-3-09)^7 \\ &:= (1+7-2+4-9+8-7+6+30-9)^7 & := (-1+7-2-49-8+76-3+09)^7 \\ &:= (1-7+2-4+9+8-7+6+30-9)^7 & := (1+7+2+49+8+7-6-30-9)^7 \\ &:= (-1+7+2+4-9-8+7+6+30-9)^7 & := (1+7-2+49+8-7-6-30+9)^7 \\ &:= (-1-7-2+4+9-8+7+6+30-9)^7 & := (-1+7+2+49-8+7-6-30+9)^7 \\ &:= (1-7-2+4-9+8+7+6+30-9)^7 & := (1-7-2+49+8+7-6-30+9)^7 \\ &:= (1+7-2-4+9-8-7-6+30+9)^7 & := (1+7+2+49-8-7+6-30+9)^7 \\ &:= (-1+7+2-4-9+8-7-6+30+9)^7 & := (-1-7+2+49+8-7+6-30+9)^7 \\ &:= (-1-7-2-4+9+8-7-6+30+9)^7 & := (1-7+2+49-8+7+6-30+9)^7 \\ &:= (1+7+2-4-9-8+7-6+30+9)^7 & := (1+7-2+4+98-7-63-09)^7 \\ &:= (1-7-2-4+9-8+7-6+30+9)^7 & := (1-7-2+4+98+7-63-09)^7 \\ &:= (-1-7+2-4-9+8+7-6+30+9)^7 & := (1-7+2-4+98-7-63+09)^7 \\ &:= (-1+7-2+4-9-8-7+6+30+9)^7 & := (1-7-2+4-9+87-6-30-9)^7 \\ &:= (-1-7+2-4+9-8-7+6+30+9)^7 & := (-17+2-49+87-6+3+09)^7 \\ &:= (1-7+2-4-9+8-7+6+30+9)^7 & := (17+2+49+8+7-63+09)^7 \\ &:= (-1-7-2+4-9-8+7+6+30+9)^7 & := (17-2+4+98-76-3-09)^7 \\ &:= (17+24-9+8+7-6-3-09)^7 & := (17+2+4-9+87-63-09)^7 \\ &:= (17+24+9-8-7+6-3-09)^7 & := (1+72+49-87+6-3-09)^7 \\ &:= (17+24-9-8-7+6-3+09)^7 & := (-1-72+49-8+7+63-09)^7 \\ &:= (-17+24+9+8-7+6-3+09)^7 & := (-1-72-4+98-7-6+30-9)^7 \\ &:= (17-24+9+8+7+6-3+09)^7 & := (-1+72+4-98+7+6+30+9)^7 \\ &:= (-17+2+49+8-7+6-3-09)^7 & := (-1+72-4+9+8-76+30-9)^7 \\ &:= (-17-2+49-8+7+6+3-09)^7 & := (-1-72+4+9-8+76+30-9)^7 \\ &:= (-17-2+49-8+7-6-3+09)^7 & := (1-72+4-9+8+76+30-9)^7 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 &:= (-1 + 72 - 4 - 9 + 8 - 76 + 30 + 9)^7 \\
 &:= (-1 - 72 + 4 - 9 - 8 + 76 + 30 + 9)^7 \\
 &:= (1 + 7 - 24 - 9 + 87 + 6 - 30 - 9)^7 \\
 &:= (1 + 7 - 2 - 49 + 87 + 6 - 30 + 9)^7 \\
 &:= (-1 - 7 - 2 - 4 + 98 - 76 + 30 - 9)^7 \\
 &:= (-1 + 7 + 2 + 4 - 98 + 76 + 30 + 9)^7 \\
 &:= (17 - 24 - 9 + 8 + 76 - 30 - 9)^7 \\
 &:= (17 - 2 - 49 + 8 + 76 - 30 + 9)^7 \\
 &:= (-1 + 7 + 24 - 98 + 76 + 30 - 9)^7 \\
 &:= (-1 - 7 - 24 + 98 - 76 + 30 + 9)^7 \\
 &:= (1 + 7 + 249 + 87 - 6 - 309)^7 \\
 \mathbf{17253512704} &:= (17 + 2535 + 1 + 27 + 04)^3 \\
 &:= (1 - 72 - 53 + 5 - 1 + 2704)^3 \\
 &:= (-1 - 72 - 53 + 5 + 1 + 2704)^3 \\
 &:= (1 - 72 + 5 - 3 - 51 + 2704)^3 \\
 \mathbf{17353862469} &:= (1735 + 3 + 862 + 4 - 6 - 9)^3 \\
 \mathbf{17363069361} &:= (-17 + 363 + 06 + 9 - 3 + 6 - 1)^4 \\
 &:= (17 + 363 - 06 - 9 + 3 - 6 + 1)^4 \\
 &:= (17 - 3 + 6 - 3 - 06 - 9 + 361)^4 \\
 &:= (17 + 3 - 6 + 3 - 06 - 9 + 361)^4 \\
 &:= (17 - 3 - 6 - 3 + 06 - 9 + 361)^4 \\
 &:= (1 + 73 - 6 + 306 - 9 + 3 - 6 + 1)^4 \\
 &:= (1 + 7 + 36 + 306 + 9 - 3 + 6 + 1)^4 \\
 &:= (1 + 7 - 3 + 6 + 306 + 9 + 36 + 1)^4 \\
 &:= (1 + 7 + 3 + 6 - 30 + 6 + 9 + 361)^4 \\
 &:= (17 - 3 - 6 + 306 - 9 - 3 + 61)^4 \\
 &:= (1 + 73 - 6 + 3 - 069 + 361)^4 \\
 &:= (-173 + 630 + 6 - 93 - 6 - 1)^4 \\
 &:= (-173 + 630 - 6 - 93 + 6 - 1)^4 \\
 &:= (173 + 63 + 069 - 3 + 61)^4 \\
 \mathbf{17413177681} &:= (174 + 131776 + 8 + 1)^2 \\
 \mathbf{17414258688} &:= (-17 + 4 - 1 + 4 + 2586 + 8 + 8)^3 \\
 &:= (1 + 7 - 4 - 14 + 2586 + 8 + 8)^3 \\
 \mathbf{17434421857} &:= (1743 - 4 - 4 + 2 - 1 + 857)^3 \\
 &:= (-1 + 743 - 4 - 4 + 2 + 1857)^3 \\
 \mathbf{17555190016} &:= (-1 + 7 + 555 - 190 - 01 - 6)^4 \\
 &:= (1 - 7 + 555 - 190 - 01 + 6)^4 \\
 &:= (-1 - 7 + 555 - 190 + 01 + 6)^4 \\
 &:= (17 + 5 - 551 + 900 - 1 - 6)^4 \\
 &:= (1 - 7 + 5 - 551 + 900 + 16)^4 \\
 &:= (-17 + 555 - 190 + 016)^4 \\
 \mathbf{17596287801} &:= (17 - 5 + 9 + 6 + 2 + 8 + 7 + 8 - 01)^6 \\
 &:= (17 + 5 + 9 - 6 + 2 + 8 + 7 + 8 + 01)^6 \\
 &:= (-1 + 75 + 9 - 6 - 2 - 8 - 7 - 8 - 01)^6 \\
 &:= (1 + 75 - 9 + 6 + 2 - 8 - 7 - 8 - 01)^6 \\
 &:= (1 + 75 - 9 - 6 - 2 + 8 - 7 - 8 - 01)^6 \\
 &:= (-1 + 75 - 9 - 6 + 2 - 8 + 7 - 8 - 01)^6 \\
 &:= (1 + 75 - 9 - 6 - 2 - 8 - 7 + 8 - 01)^6 \\
 &:= (-1 + 75 - 9 + 6 + 2 - 8 - 7 - 8 + 01)^6 \\
 &:= (-1 + 75 - 9 - 6 - 2 + 8 - 7 - 8 + 01)^6 \\
 &:= (-1 + 75 - 9 - 6 - 2 - 8 - 7 + 8 + 01)^6 \\
 &:= (1 + 7 + 59 + 6 + 2 - 8 - 7 - 8 - 01)^6 \\
 &:= (1 + 7 + 59 - 6 - 2 + 8 - 7 - 8 - 01)^6 \\
 &:= (-1 - 7 + 59 + 6 + 2 + 8 - 7 - 8 - 01)^6 \\
 &:= (-1 + 7 + 59 - 6 + 2 - 8 + 7 - 8 - 01)^6 \\
 &:= (1 - 7 + 59 + 6 + 2 - 8 + 7 - 8 - 01)^6 \\
 &:= (1 - 7 + 59 - 6 - 2 + 8 + 7 - 8 - 01)^6 \\
 &:= (1 + 7 + 59 - 6 - 2 - 8 - 7 + 8 - 01)^6 \\
 &:= (-1 - 7 + 59 + 6 + 2 - 8 - 7 + 8 - 01)^6 \\
 &:= (-1 - 7 + 59 - 6 - 2 + 8 - 7 + 8 - 01)^6 \\
 &:= (1 - 7 + 59 - 6 - 2 + 8 - 7 - 8 + 01)^6 \\
 &:= (1 + 7 + 59 - 6 - 2 - 8 + 7 - 8 + 01)^6 \\
 &:= (-1 - 7 + 59 + 6 + 2 - 8 - 7 - 8 + 01)^6 \\
 &:= (-1 - 7 + 59 - 6 - 2 + 8 - 7 - 8 + 01)^6 \\
 &:= (1 - 7 + 59 + 6 - 2 + 8 - 7 - 8 + 01)^6 \\
 &:= (1 + 7 + 59 - 6 - 2 - 8 + 7 - 8 + 01)^6 \\
 &:= (-1 - 7 + 59 + 6 + 2 - 8 - 7 - 8 + 01)^6 \\
 &:= (-1 - 7 + 59 - 6 - 2 + 8 - 7 + 8 + 01)^6 \\
 &:= (1 - 7 + 59 + 6 - 2 - 8 - 7 + 8 + 01)^6 \\
 &:= (-1 - 7 + 59 - 6 - 2 - 8 + 7 + 8 + 01)^6 \\
 &:= (1 - 7 + 5 - 9 - 6 - 2 - 8 + 78 - 01)^6 \\
 &:= (-1 - 7 - 5 - 9 + 6 - 2 - 8 + 78 - 01)^6 \\
 &:= (-1 - 7 + 5 - 9 - 6 - 2 - 8 + 78 + 01)^6 \\
 &:= (17 + 5 - 9 + 62 - 8 - 7 - 8 - 01)^6 \\
 &:= (-17 + 5 + 9 + 62 + 8 - 7 - 8 - 01)^6
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 &:= (-17+5+9+62-8-7+8-01)^6 \\
 &:= (-17+5+9+62-8+7-8+01)^6 \\
 &:= (-17+5-9+62+8-7+8+01)^6 \\
 &:= (17+5+9-6+28+7-8-01)^6 \\
 &:= (17-5-9+6+28+7+8-01)^6 \\
 &:= (17+5+9+6+28-7-8+01)^6 \\
 &:= (17+5-9-6+28+7+8+01)^6 \\
 &:= (-17-5-9+6-2+87-8-01)^6 \\
 &:= (-17+5-9-6-2+87-8+01)^6 \\
 &:= (-17+5-9+6+2-8-7+80-1)^6 \\
 &:= (-17+5-9-6-2+8-7+80-1)^6 \\
 &:= (-17-5-9+6-2-8+7+80-1)^6 \\
 &:= (-17+5-9-6-2-8+7+80+1)^6 \\
 &:= (1+75+9-6-28-7+8-01)^6 \\
 &:= (1+75+9-6-28+7-8+01)^6 \\
 &:= (-1+75+9-6-28-7+8+01)^6 \\
 &:= (1+7-59+6+2+87+8-01)^6 \\
 &:= (-1+7-59+6+2+87+8+01)^6 \\
 &:= (1+7-59+6+2+8+7+80-1)^6 \\
 &:= (-1+7-59+6+2+8+7+80+1)^6 \\
 &:= (1-7+5+96-28-7-8-01)^6 \\
 &:= (-1-7+5+96-28-7-8+01)^6 \\
 &:= (1-7+5+9-6-28+78-01)^6 \\
 &:= (-1-7-5+9+6-28+78-01)^6 \\
 &:= (-1-7+5+9-6-28+78+01)^6 \\
 &:= (1+7-5-9+6-28+78+01)^6 \\
 &:= (17-59+6+2+8+78-01)^6 \\
 &:= (17+5+96+2+8-78+01)^6 \\
 &:= (17+5+9-62+8-7+80+1)^6 \\
 &:= (17+5-9-6-28-7+80-1)^6 \\
 &:= (-17-5+9+6-28+7+80-1)^6 \\
 &:= (-17+5+9-6-28+7+80+1)^6 \\
 &:= (1+75-96+2-8+78-01)^6 \\
 &:= (-1+75-96+2-8+78+01)^6 \\
 &:= (1+75+9+62-87-8-01)^6 \\
 &:= (-1+75+9+62-87-8+01)^6 \\
 &:= (1+75-9+62-87+8+01)^6 \\
 &:= (1+75+9+62-8-7-80-1)^6
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 &:= (-1+75+9+62-8-7-80+1)^6 \\
 &:= (1+75-9+62+8-7-80+1)^6 \\
 &:= (1+75-9-6-2-87+80-1)^6 \\
 &:= (-1+75-9-6-2-87+80+1)^6 \\
 &:= (1+7+59+62-87+8+01)^6 \\
 &:= (1+7+59+62+8-7-80+1)^6 \\
 &:= (1-7+59+62+8+7-80+1)^6 \\
 &:= (1-7+59-6-2+87-80-1)^6 \\
 &:= (1+7+59-6-2-87+80-1)^6 \\
 &:= (-1-7+59+6+2-87+80-1)^6 \\
 &:= (-1-7+59-6-2+87-80+1)^6 \\
 &:= (-1+7+59-6-2-87+80+1)^6 \\
 &:= (1-7+59+6-2-87+80+1)^6 \\
 &:= (-1+7-5+96+28+7-80-1)^6 \\
 &:= (1+7+5+96+28-7-80+1)^6 \\
 &:= (1-7+5+96+28+7-80+1)^6 \\
 &:= (175-96-28-7+8-01)^6 \\
 &:= (175-96-28+7-8+01)^6 \\
 &:= (175+9-62+8-78-01)^6 \\
 &:= (17+59+62-8-78-01)^6 \\
 &:= (-17+59-62-8+78+01)^6 \\
 &:= (-17+5+9+62-87+80-1)^6 \\
 &:= (-1+7-59-62+87+80-1)^6 \\
 &:= (-1+759-628-78-01)^6 \\
 &:= (1+759+62+8-780+1)^6 \\
 &:= (1759+6+28+7+801)^3 \\
 &**17613271225** := (-1+7-6+132712-2+5)^2 \\
 &:= (1-7+6+132712-2+5)^2 \\
 &**17623416832** := (17+6+2-3+4-1+6+83-2)^5 \\
 &:= (17+6+2+3-4+1+6+83-2)^5 \\
 &:= (17+6+2+3+4+1-6+83+2)^5 \\
 &:= (17+6-2-3+4-1+6+83+2)^5 \\
 &:= (17+6-2+3-4+1+6+83+2)^5 \\
 &:= (17-6+2+3+4+1+6+83+2)^5 \\
 &:= (1+76+23+4-1+6+8-3-2)^5 \\
 &:= (-1+76+23+4+1+6+8-3-2)^5 \\
 &:= (1+76+23-4+1+6+8+3-2)^5 \\
 &:= (1+76+23+4+1-6+8+3+2)^5
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} & := (-1 + 76 + 23 - 4 - 1 + 6 + 8 + 3 + 2)^5 & := (-17 + 62 + 3 - 4 - 1 + 68 + 3 - 2)^5 \\ & := (1 + 76 - 2 + 3 + 41 + 6 - 8 - 3 - 2)^5 & := (-17 + 62 - 3 + 4 - 1 + 68 - 3 + 2)^5 \\ & := (-1 + 76 + 2 - 3 + 41 - 6 + 8 - 3 - 2)^5 & := (-17 + 62 + 3 - 4 + 1 + 68 - 3 + 2)^5 \\ & := (1 + 76 - 2 - 3 + 41 + 6 - 8 + 3 - 2)^5 & := (-17 + 62 - 3 - 4 + 1 + 68 + 3 + 2)^5 \\ & := (-1 + 76 + 2 - 3 + 41 + 6 - 8 - 3 + 2)^5 & := (-17 + 62 - 3 - 4 - 1 - 6 + 83 - 2)^5 \\ & := (-1 + 76 - 2 - 3 + 41 - 6 + 8 - 3 + 2)^5 & := (17 + 6 + 23 + 4 - 1 + 68 - 3 - 2)^5 \\ & := (-1 + 76 + 2 + 3 + 41 - 6 - 8 + 3 + 2)^5 & := (17 + 6 + 23 - 4 + 1 + 68 + 3 - 2)^5 \\ & := (1 + 7 + 62 + 34 - 1 + 6 + 8 - 3 - 2)^5 & := (17 - 6 + 23 + 4 + 1 + 68 + 3 + 2)^5 \\ & := (-1 + 7 + 62 + 34 + 1 + 6 + 8 - 3 - 2)^5 & := (17 - 6 + 23 + 4 - 1 - 6 + 83 - 2)^5 \\ & := (1 + 7 + 62 + 34 + 1 - 6 + 8 + 3 + 2)^5 & := (-17 + 6 - 2 - 3 + 41 + 6 + 83 - 2)^5 \\ & := (1 + 7 + 62 + 3 + 4 + 1 - 6 + 8 + 32)^5 & := (-1 + 76 - 23 + 41 + 6 + 8 + 3 + 2)^5 \\ & := (-1 + 7 + 62 + 3 - 4 - 1 + 6 + 8 + 32)^5 & := (1 + 76 - 23 - 4 - 1 + 68 - 3 - 2)^5 \\ & := (1 + 7 + 6 + 2 + 34 - 1 + 68 - 3 - 2)^5 & := (-1 + 76 - 23 - 4 + 1 + 68 - 3 - 2)^5 \\ & := (-1 + 7 + 6 + 2 + 34 + 1 + 68 - 3 - 2)^5 & := (1 + 76 - 2 + 34 + 16 - 8 - 3 - 2)^5 \\ & := (-1 + 7 + 6 - 2 + 34 - 1 + 68 + 3 - 2)^5 & := (-1 + 76 + 2 + 3 - 41 + 68 + 3 + 2)^5 \\ & := (1 + 7 + 6 - 2 + 34 - 1 + 68 - 3 + 2)^5 & := (1 + 76 - 2 + 3 - 41 - 6 + 83 - 2)^5 \\ & := (-1 + 7 + 6 - 2 + 34 + 1 + 68 - 3 + 2)^5 & := (-1 + 76 + 2 - 3 - 41 - 6 + 83 + 2)^5 \\ & := (1 + 7 - 6 + 2 + 34 + 1 + 68 + 3 + 2)^5 & := (1 + 76 + 2 - 3 - 4 + 16 - 8 + 32)^5 \\ & := (1 + 7 - 6 + 2 + 34 - 1 - 6 + 83 - 2)^5 & := (-1 + 76 - 2 + 3 - 4 + 16 - 8 + 32)^5 \\ & := (-1 + 7 - 6 + 2 + 34 + 1 - 6 + 83 - 2)^5 & := (1 + 7 + 62 - 34 + 1 - 6 + 83 - 2)^5 \\ & := (1 - 7 + 6 + 2 + 34 + 1 - 6 + 83 - 2)^5 & := (-1 + 7 + 62 - 34 - 1 - 6 + 83 + 2)^5 \\ & := (1 - 7 - 6 + 2 + 34 + 1 + 6 + 83 - 2)^5 & := (1 - 7 + 62 - 34 - 1 + 6 + 83 + 2)^5 \\ & := (1 + 7 - 6 - 2 + 34 - 1 - 6 + 83 + 2)^5 & := (-1 - 7 + 62 - 34 + 1 + 6 + 83 + 2)^5 \\ & := (-1 - 7 + 6 + 2 + 34 - 1 - 6 + 83 + 2)^5 & := (1 - 7 + 62 - 3 + 41 - 6 - 8 + 32)^5 \\ & := (-1 + 7 - 6 - 2 + 34 + 1 - 6 + 83 + 2)^5 & := (-1 + 7 - 62 + 3 - 4 + 168 + 3 - 2)^5 \\ & := (1 - 7 + 6 - 2 + 34 + 1 - 6 + 83 + 2)^5 & := (1 + 7 - 62 + 3 - 4 + 168 - 3 + 2)^5 \\ & := (-1 - 7 - 6 + 2 + 34 - 1 + 6 + 83 + 2)^5 & := (-1 + 7 - 62 - 3 + 4 + 168 - 3 + 2)^5 \\ & := (1 - 7 - 6 - 2 + 34 + 1 + 6 + 83 + 2)^5 & := (1 + 7 - 62 - 3 - 4 + 168 + 3 + 2)^5 \\ & := (1 + 7 + 6 + 2 + 3 - 4 + 16 + 83 - 2)^5 & := (1 - 7 - 62 + 3 + 4 + 168 + 3 + 2)^5 \\ & := (-1 + 7 + 6 + 2 - 3 + 4 + 16 + 83 - 2)^5 & := (-1 - 7 + 62 - 3 - 4 - 16 + 83 - 2)^5 \\ & := (1 + 7 + 6 - 2 + 3 - 4 + 16 + 83 + 2)^5 & := (1 + 7 + 62 + 3 + 4 - 1 + 68 - 32)^5 \\ & := (-1 + 7 + 6 - 2 - 3 + 4 + 16 + 83 + 2)^5 & := (-1 + 7 + 62 + 3 + 4 + 1 + 68 - 32)^5 \\ & := (1 + 7 - 6 + 2 + 3 + 4 + 16 + 83 + 2)^5 & := (1 + 7 + 6 + 23 + 41 - 6 + 8 + 32)^5 \\ & := (-1 + 7 + 6 + 2 + 3 - 4 - 1 + 68 + 32)^5 & := (1 + 7 - 6 + 23 + 41 + 6 + 8 + 32)^5 \\ & := (1 + 7 + 6 - 2 - 3 + 4 - 1 + 68 + 32)^5 & := (1 - 7 - 6 + 23 + 4 + 16 + 83 - 2)^5 \\ & := (1 + 7 + 6 - 2 + 3 - 4 + 1 + 68 + 32)^5 & := (-1 - 7 - 6 + 23 + 4 - 1 + 68 + 32)^5 \\ & := (-1 + 7 + 6 - 2 - 3 + 4 + 1 + 68 + 32)^5 & := (176 - 23 + 4 + 1 - 6 - 8 - 32)^5 \\ & := (1 + 7 - 6 + 2 + 3 + 4 + 1 + 68 + 32)^5 & := (176 - 2 - 3 - 41 + 6 + 8 - 32)^5 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 &:= (176 - 2 + 3 + 4 + 16 - 83 - 2)^5 & &:= (-1 - 7 + 75 + 9 - 1 + 5 + 2529)^3 \\
 &:= (176 + 2 + 3 - 4 + 16 - 83 + 2)^5 & &:= (1 + 7 + 75 - 9 + 1 + 5 + 2529)^3 \\
 &:= (-17 + 62 + 34 - 1 - 6 + 8 + 32)^5 & &:= (1 + 7 + 7 + 59 + 1 + 5 + 2529)^3 \\
 &:= (17 + 62 - 3 - 4 + 16 - 8 + 32)^5 & &:= (-1 + 7 - 7 - 5 + 91 - 5 + 2529)^3 \\
 &:= (-17 - 6 + 2 - 34 + 168 - 3 + 2)^5 & &:= (-1 - 7 + 7 - 5 + 91 - 5 + 2529)^3 \\
 &:= (17 - 6 + 2 + 34 - 16 + 83 - 2)^5 & & \mathbf{17777155561} := (-1 + 77771 + 55561)^2 \\
 &:= (17 - 6 - 2 + 34 - 16 + 83 + 2)^5 & & \mathbf{17777955556} := (-1 + 77779 + 55556)^2 \\
 &:= (-17 - 6 + 2 + 34 - 1 + 68 + 32)^5 & & \mathbf{17800025131} := (17 + 80 + 002513 + 1)^3 \\
 &:= (-17 - 6 - 2 - 3 + 4 + 168 - 32)^5 & & \mathbf{17881958375} := (1788 - 1 - 9 + 5 + 837 - 5)^3 \\
 &:= (1 - 76 + 234 - 1 - 6 - 8 - 32)^5 & & \mathbf{17881958375} := (1788 - 1 - 9 - 5 + 837 + 5)^3 \\
 &:= (-1 - 76 + 234 + 1 - 6 - 8 - 32)^5 & & \mathbf{17944209936} := (17 + 9 + 442 - 099 + 3 - 6)^4 \\
 &:= (1 + 76 + 23 + 4 - 16 - 8 + 32)^5 & & &:= (1 + 794 - 420 + 9 - 9 - 3 - 6)^4 \\
 &:= (-1 + 76 - 23 + 4 + 16 + 8 + 32)^5 & & &:= (1 + 794 - 420 - 9 + 9 - 3 - 6)^4 \\
 &:= (-1 + 76 + 2 - 34 - 16 + 83 + 2)^5 & & &:= (1 + 794 - 420 - 9 - 9 + 3 + 6)^4 \\
 &:= (1 + 7 + 62 + 34 - 16 - 8 + 32)^5 & & &:= (-1 + 79 - 4 - 4 + 209 + 93 - 6)^4 \\
 &:= (-1 - 7 + 62 + 34 - 16 + 8 + 32)^5 & & &:= (17 + 9 + 44 + 209 + 93 - 6)^4 \\
 &:= (1 - 7 + 62 - 3 - 41 + 68 + 32)^5 & & &:= (-179 - 442 + 0993 - 6)^4 \\
 &:= (-1 + 7 + 6 + 23 + 41 + 68 - 32)^5 & & \mathbf{17964142659} := (1 + 7 - 9 + 6 - 41 - 4 + 2659)^3 \\
 &:= (-1 + 7 + 6 - 2 - 34 + 168 - 32)^5 & & &:= (1 - 7 + 9 - 6 - 41 + 4 + 2659)^3 \\
 &:= (176 + 23 - 41 - 6 - 8 - 32)^5 & & \mathbf{18025945848} := (1 - 8 + 02594 - 5 - 8 + 48)^3 \\
 &:= (176 - 23 - 4 - 1 - 68 + 32)^5 & & &:= (-18 + 02594 + 58 - 4 - 8)^3 \\
 &:= (176 - 2 - 3 + 41 - 68 - 32)^5 & & &:= (-1 + 80 + 2594 + 5 - 8 - 48)^3 \\
 &:= (-17 + 62 - 34 + 16 + 83 + 2)^5 & & &:= (18 + 02594 + 58 - 48)^3 \\
 &:= (-17 + 62 - 34 + 1 + 68 + 32)^5 & & \mathbf{18129265883} := (-18 - 1 + 2 - 9 + 2658 - 8 + 3)^3 \\
 &:= (-17 - 6 + 234 + 1 - 68 - 32)^5 & & &:= (1 + 812 + 926 + 5 + 883)^3 \\
 &:= (1 - 762 + 34 + 1 + 6 + 832)^5 & & \mathbf{18141126721} := (1 - 8 - 1 + 411 - 26 - 7 - 2 - 1)^4 \\
 &:= (1 + 7 - 62 - 34 + 168 + 32)^5 & & &:= (-1 - 8 + 1 + 411 - 26 - 7 - 2 - 1)^4 \\
 &:= (1 + 7 + 6 + 234 - 168 + 32)^5 & & &:= (-1 - 8 - 1 + 411 - 26 - 7 - 2 + 1)^4 \\
 & \mathbf{17718342543} := (1 + 77 + 1 - 8 - 3 - 4 + 2543)^3 & & &:= (1 - 8 - 1 + 411 - 2 - 6 - 7 - 21)^4 \\
 &:= (1 + 7 + 71 - 8 - 3 - 4 + 2543)^3 & & &:= (-1 - 8 + 1 + 411 - 2 - 6 - 7 - 21)^4 \\
 &:= (-1 - 7 + 71 + 8 - 3 - 4 + 2543)^3 & & &:= (18 + 1 + 411 + 2 + 6 - 72 + 1)^4 \\
 &:= (1 - 7 + 71 - 8 + 3 + 4 + 2543)^3 & & &:= (1 - 81 + 411 + 26 + 7 + 2 + 1)^4 \\
 &:= (1771 + 834 - 2 + 5 - 4 + 3)^3 & & &:= (1 - 81 + 411 + 2 + 6 + 7 + 21)^4 \\
 &:= (-17 - 7 + 1 + 83 + 4 + 2543)^3 & & &:= (1 + 81 + 4 + 11 + 267 + 2 + 1)^4 \\
 &:= (1 - 771 + 834 + 2543)^3 & & &:= (1 + 8 + 1 + 411 - 26 - 7 - 21)^4 \\
 & \mathbf{17748900625} := (1 + 77 + 4 + 8 + 900 - 625)^4 & & &:= (181 + 4 + 112 + 67 + 2 + 1)^4 \\
 &:= (1 + 7 + 74 + 8 + 900 - 625)^4 & & \mathbf{18295397875} := (1829 - 53 - 9 - 7 + 875)^3 \\
 & \mathbf{17759152529} := (1 + 77 + 5 - 9 + 1 + 5 + 2529)^3 & & \mathbf{18337088853} := (1833 + 708 + 88 + 5 + 3)^3
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 &:= (1833 + 708 + 8 + 85 + 3)^3 & &:= (-1 + 84 + 24 + 3 + 5 - 1 - 7 + 9 - 3)^5 \\
 &:= (1833 - 70 - 8 + 885 - 3)^3 & &:= (1 + 84 + 24 - 3 - 5 - 1 + 7 + 9 - 3)^5 \\
 &:= (-183 + 3708 - 885 - 3)^3 & &:= (-1 + 84 + 24 - 3 - 5 + 1 + 7 + 9 - 3)^5 \\
 \mathbf{18339659776} &:= (-1 + 8 + 339 + 6 + 5 - 9 + 7 + 7 + 6)^4 & &:= (1 + 84 + 24 - 3 + 5 + 1 + 7 - 9 + 3)^5 \\
 &:= (1 + 8 - 3 + 396 - 5 - 9 - 7 - 7 - 6)^4 & &:= (-1 + 84 + 24 - 3 + 5 - 1 - 7 + 9 + 3)^5 \\
 &:= (1 - 8 + 3 + 396 + 5 - 9 - 7 - 7 - 6)^4 & &:= (1 + 84 + 24 + 3 - 5 + 1 - 7 + 9 + 3)^5 \\
 &:= (-1 - 8 - 3 + 396 - 5 + 9 - 7 - 7 - 6)^4 & &:= (-1 + 84 + 2 + 43 + 5 - 1 - 7 - 9 - 3)^5 \\
 &:= (-1 - 8 + 3 + 396 - 5 - 9 - 7 - 7 + 6)^4 & &:= (1 + 84 - 2 + 43 + 5 + 1 - 7 - 9 - 3)^5 \\
 &:= (1 - 8 + 339 + 65 - 9 - 7 - 7 - 6)^4 & &:= (-1 + 84 - 2 + 43 - 5 - 1 + 7 - 9 - 3)^5 \\
 &:= (-18 + 339 - 6 + 59 + 7 - 7 - 6)^4 & &:= (1 + 84 + 2 + 43 - 5 + 1 - 7 - 9 + 3)^5 \\
 &:= (-18 + 339 - 6 + 59 - 7 + 7 - 6)^4 & &:= (1 + 8 + 42 + 43 + 5 + 1 + 7 + 9 - 3)^5 \\
 &:= (-1 + 8 + 339 + 6 - 5 + 97 - 76)^4 & &:= (1 + 8 - 4 + 2 - 4 + 35 - 1 + 79 - 3)^5 \\
 &:= (1 + 8 + 339 - 6 + 5 + 97 - 76)^4 & &:= (1 - 8 + 4 + 2 + 4 + 35 - 1 + 79 - 3)^5 \\
 &:= (1 - 8 + 3 + 396 + 59 - 77 - 6)^4 & &:= (-1 + 8 - 4 + 2 - 4 + 35 + 1 + 79 - 3)^5 \\
 &:= (1 - 8 + 3 + 396 + 59 - 7 - 76)^4 & &:= (-1 - 8 + 4 + 2 + 4 + 35 + 1 + 79 - 3)^5 \\
 &:= (-1 - 8 - 3 + 396 + 5 - 97 + 76)^4 & &:= (-1 + 8 - 4 - 2 - 4 + 35 - 1 + 79 + 3)^5 \\
 &:= (-183 - 39 + 6 + 597 - 7 - 6)^4 & &:= (-1 - 8 + 4 - 2 + 4 + 35 - 1 + 79 + 3)^5 \\
 &:= (-183 - 39 - 6 + 597 - 7 + 6)^4 & &:= (1 - 8 + 4 + 2 - 4 + 35 + 1 + 79 + 3)^5 \\
 &:= (-183 - 39 + 659 + 7 - 76)^4 & &:= (1 - 8 - 4 + 2 + 4 + 35 + 1 + 79 + 3)^5 \\
 \mathbf{18357958072} &:= (1835 + 795 + 80 - 72)^3 & &:= (-1 - 8 + 4 + 2 - 4 + 35 - 1 - 7 + 93)^5 \\
 \mathbf{18378843119} &:= (-18 - 378 - 84 + 3119)^3 & &:= (-1 - 8 - 4 + 2 + 4 + 35 - 1 - 7 + 93)^5 \\
 \mathbf{18424351793} &:= (1 + 84 + 2 + 4 + 3 + 5 + 1 + 7 + 9 - 3)^5 & &:= (1 - 8 + 4 - 2 - 4 + 35 + 1 - 7 + 93)^5 \\
 &:= (1 + 84 - 2 + 4 + 3 + 5 - 1 + 7 + 9 + 3)^5 & &:= (1 - 8 - 4 - 2 + 4 + 35 + 1 - 7 + 93)^5 \\
 &:= (1 + 84 + 2 + 4 - 3 + 5 + 1 + 7 + 9 + 3)^5 & &:= (-1 - 8 + 4 - 2 - 4 - 3 + 51 + 79 - 3)^5 \\
 &:= (-1 + 84 - 2 + 4 + 3 + 5 + 1 + 7 + 9 + 3)^5 & &:= (-1 - 8 - 4 - 2 + 4 - 3 + 51 + 79 - 3)^5 \\
 &:= (18 + 4 + 2 + 4 + 3 + 5 + 1 + 79 - 3)^5 & &:= (1 - 8 - 4 - 2 - 4 + 3 + 51 + 79 - 3)^5 \\
 &:= (18 + 4 - 2 + 4 + 3 + 5 - 1 + 79 + 3)^5 & &:= (1 - 8 - 4 - 2 - 4 - 3 + 51 + 79 + 3)^5 \\
 &:= (18 + 4 + 2 + 4 - 3 + 5 + 1 + 79 + 3)^5 & &:= (1 + 8 + 4 + 2 - 4 - 3 - 5 + 17 + 93)^5 \\
 &:= (18 + 4 + 2 - 4 + 3 + 5 - 1 - 7 + 93)^5 & &:= (1 + 8 - 4 + 2 + 4 - 3 - 5 + 17 + 93)^5 \\
 &:= (18 - 4 + 2 + 4 + 3 + 5 - 1 - 7 + 93)^5 & &:= (-1 + 8 + 4 - 2 - 4 + 3 - 5 + 17 + 93)^5 \\
 &:= (18 + 4 + 2 + 4 + 3 - 5 + 1 - 7 + 93)^5 & &:= (-1 + 8 - 4 - 2 + 4 + 3 - 5 + 17 + 93)^5 \\
 &:= (18 + 4 - 2 + 4 - 3 + 5 + 1 - 7 + 93)^5 & &:= (-1 + 8 - 4 + 2 - 4 - 3 + 5 + 17 + 93)^5 \\
 &:= (18 + 4 - 2 - 4 + 3 - 5 - 1 + 7 + 93)^5 & &:= (-1 - 8 + 4 + 2 + 4 - 3 + 5 + 17 + 93)^5 \\
 &:= (18 - 4 - 2 + 4 + 3 - 5 - 1 + 7 + 93)^5 & &:= (1 - 8 + 4 + 2 - 4 + 3 + 5 + 17 + 93)^5 \\
 &:= (18 - 4 + 2 - 4 - 3 + 5 - 1 + 7 + 93)^5 & &:= (1 - 8 - 4 + 2 + 4 + 3 + 5 + 17 + 93)^5 \\
 &:= (18 + 4 + 2 - 4 - 3 - 5 + 1 + 7 + 93)^5 & &:= (184 - 2 + 4 - 3 - 51 - 7 - 9 - 3)^5 \\
 &:= (18 - 4 + 2 + 4 - 3 - 5 + 1 + 7 + 93)^5 & &:= (184 - 2 + 4 + 3 + 5 + 1 - 79 - 3)^5 \\
 &:= (1 + 84 + 24 + 3 + 5 + 1 + 7 - 9 - 3)^5 & &:= (184 + 2 - 4 + 3 + 5 - 1 - 79 + 3)^5
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} &:= (184 + 2 + 4 + 3 - 5 + 1 - 79 + 3)^5 &:= (-1 + 8 - 4 - 24 + 35 - 1 + 7 + 93)^5 \\ &:= (184 - 2 + 4 - 3 + 5 + 1 - 79 + 3)^5 &:= (1 + 8 + 4 - 24 - 3 + 51 + 79 - 3)^5 \\ &:= (184 + 2 + 4 + 3 + 5 + 1 + 7 - 93)^5 &:= (-1 + 8 - 4 - 24 - 3 + 51 - 7 + 93)^5 \\ &:= (18 + 42 + 4 + 35 + 1 + 7 + 9 - 3)^5 &:= (1 - 8 + 4 - 24 + 3 + 51 - 7 + 93)^5 \\ &:= (18 + 42 + 4 + 3 + 51 + 7 - 9 - 3)^5 &:= (1 - 8 - 4 - 24 - 3 + 51 + 7 + 93)^5 \\ &:= (18 + 42 + 4 - 3 + 51 + 7 - 9 + 3)^5 &:= (-1 + 8 + 4 + 24 - 3 + 5 - 17 + 93)^5 \\ &:= (-18 + 42 + 4 + 3 + 5 + 1 + 79 - 3)^5 &:= (1 + 8 - 4 + 24 + 3 + 5 - 17 + 93)^5 \\ &:= (-18 + 42 + 4 - 3 + 5 + 1 + 79 + 3)^5 &:= (-1 - 8 - 4 + 24 - 3 - 5 + 17 + 93)^5 \\ &:= (-18 + 42 - 4 + 3 + 5 - 1 - 7 + 93)^5 &:= (-1 + 8 - 4 + 2 - 43 + 51 + 7 + 93)^5 \\ &:= (-18 + 42 + 4 + 3 - 5 + 1 - 7 + 93)^5 &:= (-1 - 8 - 4 - 2 - 43 - 5 + 179 - 3)^5 \\ &:= (-18 + 42 - 4 - 3 - 5 + 1 + 7 + 93)^5 &:= (1 - 8 + 4 + 2 + 43 - 5 - 17 + 93)^5 \\ &:= (18 + 4 + 24 + 3 + 51 + 7 + 9 - 3)^5 &:= (-1 - 8 - 4 + 2 + 43 + 5 - 17 + 93)^5 \\ &:= (18 + 4 + 24 - 3 + 51 + 7 + 9 + 3)^5 &:= (184 - 24 - 35 + 1 - 7 - 9 + 3)^5 \\ &:= (18 + 4 + 24 - 3 - 5 - 1 + 79 - 3)^5 &:= (184 - 24 + 3 - 51 + 7 - 9 + 3)^5 \\ &:= (18 - 4 + 24 + 3 - 5 + 1 + 79 - 3)^5 &:= (184 + 24 - 3 - 5 - 1 + 7 - 93)^5 \\ &:= (18 - 4 + 24 - 3 - 5 + 1 + 79 + 3)^5 &:= (-18 + 42 + 43 + 51 + 7 - 9 - 3)^5 \\ &:= (-18 + 4 + 24 - 3 + 5 + 1 + 7 + 93)^5 &:= (18 + 42 + 43 + 5 + 17 - 9 - 3)^5 \\ &:= (18 + 4 + 2 + 43 + 51 + 7 - 9 - 3)^5 &:= (18 - 42 + 43 - 5 - 1 + 7 + 93)^5 \\ &:= (18 + 4 - 2 + 43 + 51 - 7 + 9 - 3)^5 &:= (18 + 42 - 43 - 5 + 1 + 7 + 93)^5 \\ &:= (-18 + 4 + 2 + 43 + 5 + 1 + 79 - 3)^5 &:= (-18 - 4 - 2 - 4 - 35 + 179 - 3)^5 \\ &:= (-18 + 4 - 2 + 43 + 5 - 1 + 79 + 3)^5 &:= (-1 + 84 + 24 + 35 - 17 - 9 - 3)^5 \\ &:= (-18 - 4 + 2 + 43 + 5 - 1 - 7 + 93)^5 &:= (1 + 84 - 24 - 35 + 1 - 7 + 93)^5 \\ &:= (-18 + 4 + 2 + 43 - 5 + 1 - 7 + 93)^5 &:= (1 + 84 - 24 + 3 - 51 + 7 + 93)^5 \\ &:= (-18 - 4 - 2 + 43 - 5 - 1 + 7 + 93)^5 &:= (-1 - 84 + 24 + 3 - 5 + 179 - 3)^5 \\ &:= (-1 + 84 + 2 + 4 + 35 - 17 + 9 - 3)^5 &:= (-1 - 84 + 24 - 3 - 5 + 179 + 3)^5 \\ &:= (1 + 84 + 2 - 4 + 35 - 17 + 9 + 3)^5 &:= (1 - 84 + 2 + 43 + 51 + 7 + 93)^5 \\ &:= (1 + 84 + 2 + 4 - 3 - 51 + 79 - 3)^5 &:= (-1 + 84 + 2 - 43 - 5 - 17 + 93)^5 \\ &:= (-1 + 84 - 2 + 4 + 3 - 51 + 79 - 3)^5 &:= (1 - 8 + 42 + 43 - 51 - 7 + 93)^5 \\ &:= (-1 + 84 - 2 + 4 - 3 - 51 + 79 + 3)^5 &:= (1 + 8 + 42 - 43 - 5 + 17 + 93)^5 \\ &:= (1 + 84 - 2 - 4 + 3 - 51 + 79 + 3)^5 &:= (-1 + 8 - 42 + 43 - 5 + 17 + 93)^5 \\ &:= (-1 + 84 + 2 - 4 - 3 - 51 - 7 + 93)^5 &:= (-1 + 8 - 4 + 243 - 51 - 79 - 3)^5 \\ &:= (1 - 84 + 2 + 4 + 3 + 5 + 179 + 3)^5 &:= (1 - 8 + 4 + 243 - 51 - 79 + 3)^5 \\ &:= (1 + 8 + 42 + 4 + 35 + 17 + 9 - 3)^5 &:= (18 - 42 - 4 - 35 + 179 - 3)^5 \\ &:= (1 + 8 + 42 - 4 - 35 + 1 + 7 + 93)^5 &:= (-18 - 4 + 24 + 35 - 17 + 93)^5 \\ &:= (-1 - 8 - 42 - 4 - 3 - 5 + 179 - 3)^5 &:= (18 - 4 + 24 - 35 + 17 + 93)^5 \\ &:= (-1 + 8 + 42 - 4 - 3 - 5 - 17 + 93)^5 &:= \mathbf{18454135716} := (184 - 54 + 135716)^2 \\ &:= (1 - 8 + 42 + 4 + 3 - 5 - 17 + 93)^5 &:= \mathbf{18462541707} := (1 - 8 + 46 + 2541 + 70 - 7)^3 \\ &:= (-1 - 8 + 42 - 4 + 3 + 5 - 17 + 93)^5 &:= \mathbf{18525482136} := (1 + 85 + 2548 + 2 + 1 + 3 + 6)^3 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 &:= (1 + 85 + 2548 + 21 - 3 - 6)^3 \\
 &:= (1852 + 5 + 4 + 821 - 36)^3 \\
 \mathbf{18539817921} &:= (-18 - 5 + 398 - 1 + 7 - 9 - 2 - 1)^4 \\
 &:= (-18 + 5 + 398 - 1 - 7 - 9 + 2 - 1)^4 \\
 &:= (-18 + 5 + 398 + 1 - 7 - 9 - 2 + 1)^4 \\
 &:= (-1 - 8 + 5 + 398 - 17 - 9 + 2 - 1)^4 \\
 &:= (1 - 8 + 5 + 398 - 17 - 9 - 2 + 1)^4 \\
 &:= (185 + 3 + 98 + 1 + 79 + 2 + 1)^4 \\
 &:= (185 + 3 + 98 - 1 - 7 + 92 - 1)^4 \\
 &:= (185 + 3 + 9 - 8 + 179 + 2 - 1)^4 \\
 &:= (185 + 3 - 9 + 8 + 179 + 2 + 1)^4 \\
 &:= (-18 - 5 + 398 - 1 + 7 + 9 - 21)^4 \\
 &:= (1 + 85 + 3 + 98 + 179 + 2 + 1)^4 \\
 &:= (1 - 8 + 539 - 81 - 79 - 2 - 1)^4 \\
 &:= (-1 - 8 + 539 - 81 - 79 - 2 + 1)^4 \\
 &:= (1 + 8 + 539 - 81 - 7 - 92 + 1)^4 \\
 &:= (18 + 539 - 8 - 179 - 2 + 1)^4 \\
 &:= (-18 - 5 - 398 - 1 + 792 - 1)^4 \\
 &:= (-1 - 85 + 398 - 1 + 79 - 21)^4 \\
 &:= (18 + 53 + 98 + 179 + 21)^4 \\
 \mathbf{18651364900} &:= (-1 + 86 - 5 + 136490 + 0)^2 \\
 \mathbf{18694022264} &:= (-1 - 8 + 6 - 9 + 402 + 2264)^3 \\
 \mathbf{18842330781} &:= (1884 + 2 - 3 - 3 + 0781)^3 \\
 \mathbf{18927429625} &:= (-1 + 8 + 9 + 2742 - 96 - 2 + 5)^3 \\
 &:= (-1 - 8 - 9 - 274 + 2962 - 5)^3 \\
 \mathbf{18945044881} &:= (1 - 89 + 450 + 4 + 4 + 8 - 8 + 1)^4 \\
 &:= (1 - 89 + 450 + 4 + 4 - 8 + 8 + 1)^4 \\
 &:= (1 - 89 + 450 - 4 - 4 + 8 + 8 + 1)^4 \\
 &:= (-1 - 8 - 9 + 450 - 44 - 8 - 8 - 1)^4 \\
 &:= (-1 - 8 - 9 + 450 - 4 - 48 - 8 - 1)^4 \\
 &:= (1 + 8 + 9 + 450 - 4 - 4 - 88 - 1)^4 \\
 &:= (1 - 8 + 9 + 450 + 4 + 4 - 88 - 1)^4 \\
 &:= (-1 + 8 + 9 + 450 - 4 - 4 - 88 + 1)^4 \\
 &:= (1 + 8 - 9 + 450 + 4 + 4 - 88 + 1)^4 \\
 &:= (-1 - 8 + 9 + 450 + 4 + 4 - 88 + 1)^4 \\
 &:= (1 + 8 + 9 + 450 - 4 - 4 - 8 - 81)^4 \\
 &:= (1 - 8 + 9 + 450 + 4 + 4 - 8 - 81)^4 \\
 &:= (1 - 8 + 9 + 450 - 4 - 4 + 8 - 81)^4 \\
 &:= (1 - 8 - 9 - 4 - 50 + 448 - 8 + 1)^4 \\
 &:= (-18 - 94 + 504 - 4 - 8 - 8 - 1)^4 \\
 &:= (1 - 89 - 4 + 504 - 48 + 8 - 1)^4 \\
 &:= (-1 - 89 - 4 + 504 - 48 + 8 + 1)^4 \\
 &:= (1 + 8 - 9 - 4 + 504 - 48 - 81)^4 \\
 &:= (-1 - 8 + 9 - 4 + 504 - 48 - 81)^4 \\
 &:= (1 - 8 + 9 - 4 - 504 - 4 + 881)^4 \\
 &:= (18 - 94 + 504 - 48 - 8 - 1)^4 \\
 &:= (1 + 894 + 5 - 0448 - 81)^4 \\
 &:= (1 - 8 - 9 - 450 - 44 + 881)^4 \\
 \mathbf{18948744296} &:= (1894 + 874 - 4 - 2 - 96)^3 \\
 \mathbf{19034163000} &:= (-1 + 90 - 3 - 416 + 3000)^3 \\
 \mathbf{19076968448} &:= (1907 + 69 + 684 + 4 + 8)^3 \\
 \mathbf{19150131456} &:= (1 - 91 + 5 - 01 + 3 - 1 + 456)^4 \\
 &:= (-1 - 91 + 5 + 01 + 3 - 1 + 456)^4 \\
 &:= (-1 - 91 + 5 - 01 + 3 + 1 + 456)^4 \\
 &:= (19 + 1 + 50 - 1 + 314 - 5 - 6)^4 \\
 &:= (19 - 1 + 50 + 1 + 314 - 5 - 6)^4 \\
 &:= (-1 - 91 + 501 + 3 - 1 - 45 + 6)^4 \\
 &:= (-1 + 9 - 1 + 501 + 3 - 145 + 6)^4 \\
 &:= (-191 + 501 + 3 - 1 + 4 + 56)^4 \\
 &:= (-19 - 1 - 50 - 13 - 1 + 456)^4 \\
 &:= (1 - 91 + 501 + 3 + 14 - 56)^4 \\
 \mathbf{19162771776} &:= (-19 + 1 + 6 + 2771 - 77 - 6)^3 \\
 &:= (-19 + 1 - 6 + 2771 - 77 + 6)^3 \\
 &:= (-19 + 1 + 6 + 2771 - 7 - 76)^3 \\
 &:= (-19 - 1 - 6 + 2771 + 7 - 76)^3 \\
 &:= (1 - 9 - 16 + 2771 - 77 + 6)^3 \\
 &:= (-1 - 9 - 16 + 2771 + 7 - 76)^3 \\
 \mathbf{19184262733} &:= (19 + 1 - 84 + 2 + 6 + 2733)^3 \\
 &:= (-19 + 1 - 8 - 4 - 26 + 2733)^3 \\
 &:= (1 + 9 - 18 - 42 - 6 + 2733)^3 \\
 &:= (1 - 9 - 18 - 4 - 26 + 2733)^3 \\
 \mathbf{19227292839} &:= (1 - 9 - 2 + 2729 - 28 - 3 - 9)^3 \\
 &:= (-19 + 2 + 2729 - 2 + 8 - 39)^3 \\
 &:= (-19 - 2 + 2729 + 2 + 8 - 39)^3 \\
 &:= (-1 - 9 - 227 + 2928 - 3 - 9)^3 \\
 &:= (19 - 2 + 2729 - 28 - 39)^3
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 \mathbf{19254145824} &:= (1 + 92 + 5 + 4 + 1 + 4 + 5 + 8 - 2 - 4)^5 & := (1 + 9 - 2 + 5 + 41 - 4 + 58 + 2 + 4)^5 \\
 &:= (-1 + 92 + 5 + 4 - 1 + 4 + 5 + 8 + 2 - 4)^5 & := (-1 + 9 + 2 - 5 + 41 + 4 + 58 + 2 + 4)^5 \\
 &:= (1 + 92 + 5 + 4 + 1 - 4 + 5 + 8 - 2 + 4)^5 & := (-1 - 9 + 2 - 5 - 4 + 145 - 8 - 2 - 4)^5 \\
 &:= (1 + 92 + 5 - 4 + 1 + 4 + 5 + 8 - 2 + 4)^5 & := (-1 - 9 - 2 - 5 - 4 + 145 - 8 + 2 - 4)^5 \\
 &:= (1 + 92 + 5 + 4 - 1 + 4 - 5 + 8 + 2 + 4)^5 & := (1 + 9 - 2 + 5 + 4 + 14 + 5 + 82 - 4)^5 \\
 &:= (-1 + 92 + 5 + 4 + 1 + 4 - 5 + 8 + 2 + 4)^5 & := (-1 + 9 + 2 + 5 + 4 + 14 - 5 + 82 + 4)^5 \\
 &:= (-1 + 92 + 5 + 4 - 1 - 4 + 5 + 8 + 2 + 4)^5 & := (1 + 9 - 2 + 5 - 4 + 14 + 5 + 82 + 4)^5 \\
 &:= (-1 + 92 + 5 - 4 - 1 + 4 + 5 + 8 + 2 + 4)^5 & := (-1 + 9 + 2 - 5 + 4 + 14 + 5 + 82 + 4)^5 \\
 &:= (1 + 92 - 5 + 4 - 1 + 4 + 5 + 8 + 2 + 4)^5 & := (192 - 54 - 1 - 4 - 5 - 8 - 2 - 4)^5 \\
 &:= (-1 + 92 - 5 + 4 + 1 + 4 + 5 + 8 + 2 + 4)^5 & := (192 - 5 - 4 - 1 - 4 - 58 - 2 - 4)^5 \\
 &:= (19 - 2 + 5 + 4 + 1 + 4 + 5 + 82 - 4)^5 & := (19 + 2 + 5 + 41 + 45 + 8 - 2 - 4)^5 \\
 &:= (19 + 2 + 5 + 4 - 1 + 4 - 5 + 82 + 4)^5 & := (19 - 2 + 5 + 41 + 45 + 8 + 2 - 4)^5 \\
 &:= (19 - 2 + 5 + 4 + 1 - 4 + 5 + 82 + 4)^5 & := (-19 + 2 + 5 + 41 + 4 - 5 + 82 + 4)^5 \\
 &:= (19 + 2 - 5 + 4 - 1 + 4 + 5 + 82 + 4)^5 & := (-19 + 2 - 5 + 41 + 4 + 5 + 82 + 4)^5 \\
 &:= (19 - 2 + 5 - 4 + 1 + 4 + 5 + 82 + 4)^5 & := (-19 + 2 + 5 + 4 - 1 + 45 + 82 - 4)^5 \\
 &:= (-1 + 92 + 5 + 41 - 4 - 5 - 8 - 2 - 4)^5 & := (-19 + 2 + 5 - 4 - 1 + 45 + 82 + 4)^5 \\
 &:= (1 + 92 - 5 + 41 + 4 - 5 - 8 - 2 - 4)^5 & := (-19 + 2 - 5 + 4 + 1 + 45 + 82 + 4)^5 \\
 &:= (-1 + 92 - 5 + 41 - 4 + 5 - 8 - 2 - 4)^5 & := (1 + 92 + 54 - 14 - 5 - 8 - 2 - 4)^5 \\
 &:= (1 + 92 - 5 + 41 - 4 - 5 - 8 - 2 + 4)^5 & := (-1 + 92 + 5 - 41 + 45 + 8 + 2 + 4)^5 \\
 &:= (1 + 92 - 5 - 4 - 1 + 45 - 8 - 2 - 4)^5 & := (-1 + 92 - 5 - 41 - 4 - 5 + 82 - 4)^5 \\
 &:= (-1 + 92 - 5 - 4 + 1 + 45 - 8 - 2 - 4)^5 & := (-1 + 92 + 5 + 41 + 4 + 5 - 8 - 24)^5 \\
 &:= (-1 + 92 + 5 + 4 - 1 + 4 - 5 - 8 + 24)^5 & := (1 + 92 + 5 + 41 - 4 - 5 + 8 - 24)^5 \\
 &:= (-1 + 92 - 5 + 4 - 1 + 4 + 5 - 8 + 24)^5 & := (1 + 92 - 5 + 41 - 4 + 5 + 8 - 24)^5 \\
 &:= (-1 + 92 + 5 - 4 - 1 - 4 - 5 + 8 + 24)^5 & := (-1 + 92 - 5 - 4 - 1 - 45 + 82 - 4)^5 \\
 &:= (1 + 92 - 5 + 4 - 1 - 4 - 5 + 8 + 24)^5 & := (1 + 92 + 5 + 4 - 1 + 45 - 8 - 24)^5 \\
 &:= (-1 + 92 - 5 + 4 + 1 - 4 - 5 + 8 + 24)^5 & := (-1 + 92 + 5 + 4 + 1 + 45 - 8 - 24)^5 \\
 &:= (1 + 92 - 5 - 4 - 1 + 4 - 5 + 8 + 24)^5 & := (1 + 92 - 5 - 4 + 1 + 45 + 8 - 24)^5 \\
 &:= (-1 + 92 - 5 - 4 + 1 + 4 - 5 + 8 + 24)^5 & := (1 - 9 + 25 + 41 + 4 + 58 - 2 - 4)^5 \\
 &:= (-1 + 92 - 5 - 4 - 1 - 4 + 5 + 8 + 24)^5 & := (1 - 9 + 25 + 41 - 4 + 58 - 2 + 4)^5 \\
 &:= (1 + 9 + 2 + 54 + 1 + 45 + 8 - 2 - 4)^5 & := (-1 + 9 - 25 - 4 + 145 - 8 + 2 - 4)^5 \\
 &:= (-1 + 9 + 2 + 54 - 1 + 45 + 8 + 2 - 4)^5 & := (1 - 9 - 25 - 4 + 145 + 8 + 2 - 4)^5 \\
 &:= (1 + 9 - 2 + 54 + 1 + 45 + 8 + 2 - 4)^5 & := (1 - 9 - 25 + 4 + 145 - 8 + 2 + 4)^5 \\
 &:= (-1 + 9 - 2 + 54 - 1 + 45 + 8 - 2 + 4)^5 & := (-1 - 9 + 25 + 4 + 14 - 5 + 82 + 4)^5 \\
 &:= (-1 - 9 + 2 + 54 - 1 - 4 - 5 + 82 - 4)^5 & := (-1 + 9 + 25 + 4 - 14 + 5 + 82 + 4)^5 \\
 &:= (1 - 9 - 2 + 54 + 1 - 4 - 5 + 82 - 4)^5 & := (-1 + 9 + 25 + 4 - 1 - 4 + 58 + 24)^5 \\
 &:= (1 + 9 + 2 + 5 + 41 + 4 + 58 - 2 - 4)^5 & := (-1 + 9 + 25 - 4 - 1 + 4 + 58 + 24)^5 \\
 &:= (1 + 9 - 2 + 5 + 41 + 4 + 58 + 2 - 4)^5 & := (1 - 9 + 2 + 54 + 14 + 58 - 2 - 4)^5 \\
 &:= (1 + 9 + 2 + 5 + 41 - 4 + 58 - 2 + 4)^5 & := (1 - 9 - 2 + 54 + 14 + 58 + 2 - 4)^5
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 &:= (-1 + 9 + 2 + 54 - 14 + 58 + 2 + 4)^5 \\
 &:= (1 - 9 - 2 + 5 + 41 - 4 + 58 + 24)^5 \\
 &:= (-1 - 9 + 2 - 5 + 41 + 4 + 58 + 24)^5 \\
 &:= (-1 + 9 + 2 - 5 - 4 + 145 - 8 - 24)^5 \\
 &:= (-1 - 9 + 2 + 5 + 4 + 145 - 8 - 24)^5 \\
 &:= (1 - 9 + 2 - 5 - 4 + 145 + 8 - 24)^5 \\
 &:= (192 - 54 - 1 + 4 + 5 - 8 - 24)^5 \\
 &:= (192 - 54 + 1 - 4 - 5 + 8 - 24)^5 \\
 &:= (192 - 5 + 4 + 14 - 5 - 82 - 4)^5 \\
 &:= (192 - 5 - 4 + 14 - 5 - 82 + 4)^5 \\
 &:= (192 + 5 + 4 - 14 + 5 - 82 + 4)^5 \\
 &:= (192 + 5 + 4 - 1 - 4 - 58 - 24)^5 \\
 &:= (192 + 5 - 4 - 1 + 4 - 58 - 24)^5 \\
 &:= (192 - 5 + 4 + 1 + 4 - 58 - 24)^5 \\
 &:= (19 - 25 + 41 - 4 + 5 + 82 - 4)^5 \\
 &:= (19 + 25 + 4 + 14 + 58 - 2 - 4)^5 \\
 &:= (19 + 25 - 4 + 14 + 58 - 2 + 4)^5 \\
 &:= (19 - 25 - 4 + 1 + 45 + 82 - 4)^5 \\
 &:= (19 + 2 - 54 + 145 + 8 - 2 - 4)^5 \\
 &:= (19 - 2 - 54 + 145 + 8 + 2 - 4)^5 \\
 &:= (-19 + 2 + 54 - 14 + 5 + 82 + 4)^5 \\
 &:= (19 + 2 + 54 + 1 + 4 + 58 - 24)^5 \\
 &:= (-19 + 2 + 54 - 1 - 4 + 58 + 24)^5 \\
 &:= (19 - 2 - 5 + 41 + 45 - 8 + 24)^5 \\
 &:= (19 - 2 + 5 - 4 + 14 + 58 + 24)^5 \\
 &:= (1 + 925 + 4 - 1 + 4 + 5 - 824)^5 \\
 &:= (-1 + 925 + 4 + 1 + 4 + 5 - 824)^5 \\
 &:= (1 - 92 + 54 + 145 + 8 + 2 - 4)^5 \\
 &:= (-1 + 92 - 54 - 14 + 5 + 82 + 4)^5 \\
 &:= (-1 + 92 + 54 - 1 + 4 - 58 + 24)^5 \\
 &:= (-1 + 92 - 54 - 1 - 4 + 58 + 24)^5 \\
 &:= (-1 + 92 - 5 + 41 - 45 + 8 + 24)^5 \\
 &:= (1 + 92 + 5 - 4 - 14 + 58 - 24)^5 \\
 &:= (1 - 9 + 254 - 1 - 45 - 82 - 4)^5 \\
 &:= (-1 - 9 + 254 + 1 - 45 - 82 - 4)^5 \\
 &:= (1 + 9 + 25 + 41 + 4 + 58 - 24)^5 \\
 &:= (1 + 9 + 2 + 54 + 14 + 58 - 24)^5 \\
 &:= (-1 - 9 + 2 + 54 - 14 + 58 + 24)^5
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 &:= (192 + 54 - 1 - 45 - 82 - 4)^5 \\
 &:= (19 + 254 - 145 - 8 - 2 - 4)^5 \\
 &:= (19 + 25 + 41 + 45 + 8 - 24)^5 \\
 \mathbf{19270387241} &:= (1 - 9 + 2703 - 8 - 7 - 2 + 4 - 1)^3 \\
 &:= (-1 - 9 + 2703 - 8 - 7 - 2 + 4 + 1)^3 \\
 \mathbf{19313545987} &:= (-1 + 9 + 3135 - 459 - 8 + 7)^3 \\
 &:= (1 - 9 + 3135 - 459 + 8 + 7)^3 \\
 \mathbf{19356769125} &:= (19 + 3567 + 6 - 912 + 5)^3 \\
 \mathbf{19356878641} &:= (19 + 356 + 8 - 7 + 8 - 6 - 4 - 1)^4 \\
 &:= (19 + 356 + 8 + 7 - 8 - 6 - 4 + 1)^4 \\
 &:= (19 + 356 - 8 + 7 + 8 - 6 - 4 + 1)^4 \\
 &:= (-193 + 568 - 7 + 8 - 6 + 4 - 1)^4 \\
 &:= (-193 + 568 + 7 - 8 - 6 + 4 + 1)^4 \\
 &:= (1 + 9 + 356 - 8 + 78 - 64 + 1)^4 \\
 &:= (-193 + 5 + 6 - 8 - 78 + 641)^4 \\
 &:= (19 + 356 + 87 - 86 - 4 + 1)^4 \\
 &:= (-1 + 935 - 6 + 8 + 78 - 641)^4 \\
 &:= (1 - 9 - 356 - 8 + 786 - 41)^4 \\
 \mathbf{19421724672} &:= (1 + 9 - 4 + 217 + 2467 - 2)^3 \\
 \mathbf{19486825371} &:= (1 + 94 - 8 + 68 + 2537 - 1)^3 \\
 &:= (-1 + 94 - 8 + 68 + 2537 + 1)^3 \\
 &:= (1948 + 682 + 53 + 7 + 1)^3 \\
 \mathbf{19565295376} &:= (-1 + 9 + 5 + 6 - 5 - 2 - 9 - 5 + 376)^4 \\
 &:= (1 + 9 + 5 - 6 + 5 - 2 - 9 - 5 + 376)^4 \\
 &:= (-1 + 9 - 5 + 6 + 5 - 2 - 9 - 5 + 376)^4 \\
 &:= (-1 - 9 + 5 + 6 - 5 - 2 + 9 - 5 + 376)^4 \\
 &:= (1 - 9 + 5 - 6 + 5 - 2 + 9 - 5 + 376)^4 \\
 &:= (-1 - 9 - 5 + 6 + 5 - 2 + 9 - 5 + 376)^4 \\
 &:= (-1 + 9 - 5 - 6 - 5 + 2 + 9 - 5 + 376)^4 \\
 &:= (1 + 9 + 5 - 6 - 5 - 2 - 9 + 5 + 376)^4 \\
 &:= (-1 + 9 - 5 + 6 - 5 - 2 - 9 + 5 + 376)^4 \\
 &:= (1 + 9 - 5 - 6 + 5 - 2 - 9 + 5 + 376)^4 \\
 &:= (1 - 9 + 5 - 6 - 5 - 2 + 9 + 5 + 376)^4 \\
 &:= (-1 - 9 - 5 + 6 - 5 - 2 + 9 + 5 + 376)^4 \\
 &:= (1 - 9 - 5 - 6 + 5 - 2 + 9 + 5 + 376)^4 \\
 &:= (-1 + 95 + 6 - 5 + 295 - 3 - 7 - 6)^4 \\
 &:= (1 + 95 - 6 + 5 + 295 - 3 - 7 - 6)^4 \\
 &:= (-1 + 95 - 6 - 5 + 295 - 3 - 7 + 6)^4
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 & := (-1 + 9 + 56 + 5 + 295 - 3 + 7 + 6)^4 & := (-1 - 9 - 7 + 70 - 6 + 09 - 6 + 6 - 4)^6 \\
 & := (1 + 9 - 5 + 6 - 5 + 295 - 3 + 76)^4 & := (19 - 7 - 7 + 060 - 9 + 6 - 6 - 4)^6 \\
 & := (-1 - 9 + 5 + 6 + 5 + 295 - 3 + 76)^4 & := (19 - 7 - 7 + 060 - 9 - 6 + 6 - 4)^6 \\
 & := (-1 - 9 - 5 - 6 - 5 + 29 - 5 + 376)^4 & := (-19 - 7 - 7 + 060 + 9 + 6 + 6 + 4)^6 \\
 & := (19 + 5 + 65 + 295 + 3 - 7 - 6)^4 & := (19 - 7 - 7 - 06 - 09 + 66 - 4)^6 \\
 & := (-1 + 95 + 6 - 5 - 2 - 95 + 376)^4 & := (-19 - 7 - 7 + 06 + 09 + 66 + 4)^6 \\
 & := (1 + 95 - 6 + 5 - 2 - 95 + 376)^4 & := (-19 - 7 - 7 + 06 + 09 + 6 + 64)^6 \\
 & := (-1 - 95 + 6 - 5 - 2 + 95 + 376)^4 & := (1 + 97 + 7 - 060 - 9 + 6 + 6 + 4)^6 \\
 & := (1 - 95 - 6 + 5 - 2 + 95 + 376)^4 & := (1 + 9 + 77 - 060 + 9 + 6 + 6 + 4)^6 \\
 & := (-1 + 9 + 56 - 52 - 9 - 5 + 376)^4 & := (1 + 9 + 7 + 70 - 60 + 9 + 6 + 6 + 4)^6 \\
 & := (-1 - 9 + 56 - 52 + 9 - 5 + 376)^4 & := (1 - 9 + 7 + 7 - 060 + 96 + 6 + 4)^6 \\
 & := (-195 + 652 - 9 + 5 - 3 - 76)^4 & := (19 + 7 + 7 - 060 + 9 + 66 + 4)^6 \\
 & := (-19 + 565 + 2 - 95 - 3 - 76)^4 & := (19 + 7 + 7 - 060 + 9 + 6 + 64)^6 \\
 & := (-19 + 56 - 5 - 29 - 5 + 376)^4 & := (-1 - 97 + 70 - 6 + 096 - 6 - 4)^6 \\
 & := (-1 + 956 - 529 - 53 + 7 - 6)^4 & := (-1 + 9 - 77 + 060 - 9 + 66 + 4)^6 \\
 & := (1 + 956 - 529 - 53 - 7 + 6)^4 & := (-1 - 9 - 77 + 060 + 9 + 66 + 4)^6 \\
 & := (-1 + 95 + 652 + 9 - 5 - 376)^4 & := (-1 + 9 - 77 + 060 - 9 + 6 + 64)^6 \\
 & := (1 - 9 + 5 - 652 + 953 + 76)^4 & := (-1 - 9 - 77 + 060 + 9 + 6 + 64)^6 \\
 & := (-1 + 9 - 5 + 652 + 95 - 376)^4 & := (-1 + 9 - 7 + 70 + 60 - 9 - 66 - 4)^6 \\
 \mathbf{19573852375} & := (1 - 9 - 57 + 385 + 2375)^3 & := (-1 - 9 - 7 + 70 + 60 + 9 - 66 - 4)^6 \\
 \mathbf{19601400025} & := (1 - 9 + 6 + 0140002 + 5)^2 & := (-1 + 9 - 7 - 70 + 60 - 9 + 66 + 4)^6 \\
 \mathbf{19614002500} & := (19 + 6 + 140025 + 00)^2 & := (-1 - 9 - 7 - 70 + 60 + 9 + 66 + 4)^6 \\
 \mathbf{19617462873} & := (1961 + 746 + 2 - 8 - 7 + 3)^3 & := (-1 + 9 - 7 + 70 + 60 - 9 - 6 - 64)^6 \\
 & := (1 - 96 - 1 - 74 - 6 + 2873)^3 & := (-1 - 9 - 7 + 70 + 60 + 9 - 6 - 64)^6 \\
 & := (-1 - 96 + 1 - 74 - 6 + 2873)^3 & := (-1 + 9 - 7 - 70 + 60 - 9 + 6 + 64)^6 \\
 & := (1 + 9 - 6 - 174 - 6 + 2873)^3 & := (-1 - 9 - 7 - 70 + 60 + 9 + 6 + 64)^6 \\
 \mathbf{19639292392} & := (1 - 96 + 392 + 9 + 2392)^3 & := (1 + 9 + 7 + 7 + 060 - 96 + 64)^6 \\
 \mathbf{19726772408} & := (-1 + 9 + 7 + 2677 - 2 + 4 + 08)^3 & := (-1 + 97 - 70 - 60 + 96 - 6 - 4)^6 \\
 & := (1972 + 6 + 772 - 40 - 8)^3 & := (-1 + 97 - 70 - 6 + 096 - 64)^6 \\
 & := (-1 + 972 - 677 + 2408)^3 & := (-1 + 9 - 7 + 706 + 09 - 664)^6 \\
 \mathbf{19770609664} & := (19 + 7 + 7 + 06 + 09 + 6 - 6 + 4)^6 & := (-1 - 977 + 060 + 966 + 4)^6 \\
 & := (19 + 7 + 7 + 06 + 09 - 6 + 6 + 4)^6 & := (-1 - 97 - 70 + 60 + 96 + 64)^6 \\
 & := (19 + 7 + 7 - 06 + 09 + 6 + 6 + 4)^6 & \\
 & := (-1 + 9 - 7 + 70 + 6 - 09 - 6 - 6 - 4)^6 & \mathbf{19773140689} := (-1 + 9 - 77 - 3 + 140689)^2 \\
 & := (-1 - 9 - 7 + 70 + 6 + 09 - 6 - 6 - 4)^6 & := (-1 + 9 - 7 - 73 + 140689)^2 \\
 & := (-1 + 9 - 7 + 70 - 6 - 09 + 6 - 6 - 4)^6 & \mathbf{19775390625} := (-19 + 7 - 7 + 5 + 390 + 6 - 2 - 5)^4 \\
 & := (-1 - 9 - 7 + 70 - 6 + 09 + 6 - 6 - 4)^6 & := (-19 - 7 + 7 + 5 + 390 + 6 - 2 - 5)^4 \\
 & := (-1 + 9 - 7 + 70 - 6 + 09 + 6 - 6 - 4)^6 & := (-19 + 7 - 7 - 5 + 390 + 6 - 2 + 5)^4 \\
 & := (-1 + 9 - 7 + 70 - 6 - 09 - 6 + 6 - 4)^6 & := (-19 - 7 + 7 - 5 + 390 + 6 - 2 + 5)^4
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 & := (-19 - 7 - 7 + 5 + 390 + 6 + 2 + 5)^4 & := (19 - 9 - 8 + 717 - 337 - 6)^4 \\
 & := (1 + 9 - 77 - 5 + 390 + 62 - 5)^4 & := (19 - 9 - 8 + 71 - 73 + 376)^4 \\
 & := (-1 - 9 - 77 + 5 + 390 + 62 + 5)^4 & := (-19 + 9 + 8 - 71 + 73 + 376)^4 \\
 & := (1 + 9 - 7 - 75 + 390 + 62 - 5)^4 & \mathbf{20034997696} := (-20 + 03499 - 769 + 6)^3 \\
 & := (-19 + 775 - 390 + 6 - 2 + 5)^4 & \mathbf{20057135813} := (2005 + 713 - 5 + 8 - 1 - 3)^3 \\
 & := (197 - 753 + 906 + 25)^4 & := (2005 + 713 + 5 - 8 - 1 + 3)^3 \\
 \mathbf{19792552625} & := (-19 + 7 + 92 + 5 - 5 + 2625)^3 & \mathbf{20079290232} := (-200 - 7 - 9 + 2902 + 32)^3 \\
 & := (-19 + 7 + 92 - 5 + 5 + 2625)^3 & \mathbf{20113571875} := (20 + 1 + 1 - 3 + 5 + 71 + 8 + 7 + 5)^5 \\
 & := (-19 + 79 + 25 - 5 + 2625)^3 & := (20 - 1 - 1 + 3 + 5 + 7 - 1 + 8 + 75)^5 \\
 \mathbf{19811407009} & := (-19 + 81 + 140700 - 9)^2 & := (20 + 1 + 1 - 3 + 5 + 7 + 1 + 8 + 75)^5 \\
 \mathbf{19836487243} & := (1983 - 6 + 487 + 243)^3 & := (-2 + 011 + 3 + 5 + 7 - 1 + 87 + 5)^5 \\
 \mathbf{19880486829} & := (1988 + 048 + 682 - 9)^3 & := (2 + 011 - 3 + 5 + 7 + 1 + 87 + 5)^5 \\
 \mathbf{19902511000} & := (199 + 02511 + 000)^3 & := (-2 + 01 + 13 + 5 + 7 - 1 + 87 + 5)^5 \\
 \mathbf{19987173376} & := (19 + 9 - 8 + 7 - 1 + 7 + 337 + 6)^4 & := (-2 - 01 + 13 + 5 + 7 + 1 + 87 + 5)^5 \\
 & := (19 - 9 + 8 + 7 + 1 + 7 + 337 + 6)^4 & := (2 + 01 + 1 + 35 - 7 + 1 + 87 - 5)^5 \\
 & := (19 - 9 + 8 - 7 - 1 - 7 - 3 + 376)^4 & := (-2 - 01 - 1 + 35 - 7 - 1 + 87 + 5)^5 \\
 & := (19 - 9 - 8 + 7 + 1 - 7 - 3 + 376)^4 & := (201 - 1 - 3 - 5 - 71 - 8 + 7 - 5)^5 \\
 & := (19 - 9 - 8 - 7 + 1 + 7 - 3 + 376)^4 & := (201 - 1 - 3 - 5 + 7 - 1 - 8 - 75)^5 \\
 & := (-19 + 9 + 8 + 7 - 1 - 7 + 3 + 376)^4 & := (201 + 1 - 3 + 5 - 7 + 1 - 8 - 75)^5 \\
 & := (-19 + 9 + 8 - 7 - 1 + 7 + 3 + 376)^4 & := (20 + 11 + 3 + 5 - 7 + 1 + 87 - 5)^5 \\
 & := (-19 + 9 - 8 + 7 + 1 + 7 + 3 + 376)^4 & := (20 - 11 + 3 + 5 + 7 - 1 + 87 + 5)^5 \\
 & := (-1 + 9 + 9 - 8 + 7 + 17 + 337 + 6)^4 & := (20 + 11 + 3 - 5 - 7 + 1 + 87 + 5)^5 \\
 & := (1 + 9 - 9 + 8 + 7 + 17 + 337 + 6)^4 & := (20 - 1 + 13 - 5 + 7 - 1 + 87 - 5)^5 \\
 & := (1 - 9 + 9 + 8 + 7 + 17 + 337 + 6)^4 & := (20 + 1 + 13 + 5 - 7 + 1 + 87 - 5)^5 \\
 & := (1 + 9 + 9 + 8 - 7 - 17 - 3 + 376)^4 & := (20 + 1 + 13 - 5 - 7 + 1 + 87 + 5)^5 \\
 & := (1 + 9 - 9 - 8 - 7 + 17 - 3 + 376)^4 & := (-20 + 1 + 1 + 35 + 7 - 1 + 87 + 5)^5 \\
 & := (1 - 9 + 9 - 8 - 7 + 17 - 3 + 376)^4 & := (-20 + 1 - 1 + 35 + 7 + 1 + 87 + 5)^5 \\
 & := (-1 + 9 - 9 + 8 + 7 - 17 + 3 + 376)^4 & := (-20 - 1 + 1 + 35 + 7 + 1 + 87 + 5)^5 \\
 & := (-1 - 9 + 9 + 8 + 7 - 17 + 3 + 376)^4 & := (-20 + 1 - 1 - 3 + 57 - 1 + 87 - 5)^5 \\
 & := (-1 - 9 - 9 - 8 + 7 + 17 + 3 + 376)^4 & := (-20 - 1 + 1 - 3 + 57 - 1 + 87 - 5)^5 \\
 & := (199 + 87 + 1 + 73 + 3 + 7 + 6)^4 & := (-20 - 1 - 1 - 3 + 57 + 1 + 87 - 5)^5 \\
 & := (199 + 87 + 1 + 7 + 3 + 3 + 76)^4 & := (-2 + 0113 + 5 - 7 + 18 - 7 - 5)^5 \\
 & := (1 + 99 + 87 + 173 + 3 + 7 + 6)^4 & := (-2 + 0113 - 5 - 7 + 18 - 7 + 5)^5 \\
 & := (-1 + 99 - 87 - 1 - 7 - 3 + 376)^4 & := (2 + 011 + 35 + 71 + 8 - 7 - 5)^5 \\
 & := (1 - 99 + 87 + 1 + 7 + 3 + 376)^4 & := (2 - 011 + 35 + 7 - 1 + 8 + 75)^5 \\
 & := (19 + 98 + 7 + 173 + 3 + 76)^4 & := (-2 - 011 + 3 + 57 + 1 - 8 + 75)^5 \\
 & := (-19 + 98 - 7 + 1 - 73 + 376)^4 & := (2 + 011 - 3 + 5 + 7 + 18 + 75)^5 \\
 & := (19 - 98 + 7 - 1 + 73 + 376)^4 & := (2 + 01 + 135 + 7 - 18 - 7 - 5)^5
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 &:= (2 + 01 + 135 - 7 - 18 + 7 - 5)^5 & &:= (2 + 0301 + 73 + 2352)^3 \\
 &:= (2 + 01 - 13 + 57 + 1 - 8 + 75)^5 & &:= (203 + 0173 + 2352)^3 \\
 &:= (-2 - 01 + 13 + 5 + 7 + 18 + 75)^5 & & \mathbf{20391167168} := (2039 + 1 - 16 + 716 - 8)^3 \\
 &:= (-2 - 01 - 1 - 35 + 71 + 8 + 75)^5 & & \mathbf{20408122449} := (20408 + 122449)^2 \\
 &:= (2 + 01 + 1 - 3 + 57 - 18 + 75)^5 & & \mathbf{20413566837} := (2041 + 3 + 5 - 6 + 683 + 7)^3 \\
 &:= (-2 + 01 - 1 + 3 + 57 - 18 + 75)^5 & & \mathbf{20415837456} := (-20 + 415 + 8 - 3 - 7 - 4 - 5 - 6)^4 \\
 &:= (-2 - 01 + 1 + 3 + 57 - 18 + 75)^5 & & &:= (-20 + 415 - 8 + 3 - 7 - 4 + 5 - 6)^4 \\
 &:= (20 + 113 + 5 + 7 - 18 - 7 - 5)^5 & & &:= (2 + 0415 + 8 - 3 + 7 - 45 - 6)^4 \\
 &:= (20 + 113 + 5 - 7 - 18 + 7 - 5)^5 & & &:= (-2 + 0415 + 8 + 3 - 7 - 45 + 6)^4 \\
 &:= (-20 + 113 - 5 + 7 + 18 + 7 - 5)^5 & & &:= (2 - 04 + 15 - 8 + 374 + 5 - 6)^4 \\
 &:= (20 + 113 - 5 + 7 - 18 - 7 + 5)^5 & & &:= (2 + 04 + 1 + 5 - 83 - 7 + 456)^4 \\
 &:= (20 + 113 - 5 - 7 - 18 + 7 + 5)^5 & & &:= (-2 + 04 + 1 - 5 - 83 + 7 + 456)^4 \\
 &:= (-20 + 11 + 35 + 7 - 1 + 8 + 75)^5 & & &:= (-2 - 04 - 1 + 5 - 83 + 7 + 456)^4 \\
 &:= (20 + 11 - 3 + 57 + 18 + 7 + 5)^5 & & &:= (-204 - 1 + 583 + 7 + 4 - 5 - 6)^4 \\
 &:= (-20 - 11 + 3 + 5 + 71 - 8 + 75)^5 & & &:= (-204 + 1 + 583 - 7 + 4 - 5 + 6)^4 \\
 &:= (-20 - 11 - 3 - 5 + 71 + 8 + 75)^5 & & &:= (-204 - 1 + 583 - 7 - 4 + 5 + 6)^4 \\
 &:= (20 + 11 + 3 - 5 - 7 + 18 + 75)^5 & & &:= (204 + 1 + 5 + 83 + 74 + 5 + 6)^4 \\
 &:= (-20 + 1 + 135 - 7 + 18 - 7 - 5)^5 & & &:= (20 + 415 - 8 - 3 - 7 - 45 + 6)^4 \\
 &:= (-20 - 1 + 135 + 7 - 18 + 7 + 5)^5 & & &:= (-20 - 41 - 5 - 8 + 3 - 7 + 456)^4 \\
 &:= (-20 - 1 + 13 + 57 - 1 - 8 + 75)^5 & & &:= (20 - 4 - 15 - 8 + 374 + 5 + 6)^4 \\
 &:= (-20 - 1 - 13 - 5 + 71 + 8 + 75)^5 & & &:= (20 - 4 + 1 - 5 - 83 - 7 + 456)^4 \\
 &:= (20 + 1 + 13 - 5 - 7 + 18 + 75)^5 & & &:= (2 + 0415 - 83 - 7 + 45 + 6)^4 \\
 &:= (-20 + 1 - 1 + 35 + 7 + 18 + 75)^5 & & &:= (-2 - 041 + 58 + 374 - 5 - 6)^4 \\
 &:= (-20 - 1 + 1 + 35 + 7 + 18 + 75)^5 & & &:= (2 - 041 - 5 - 8 + 374 + 56)^4 \\
 &:= (-2 - 011 - 35 + 71 + 87 + 5)^5 & & &:= (20 + 41 - 58 + 374 - 5 + 6)^4 \\
 &:= (-2 - 011 + 3 - 57 + 187 - 5)^5 & & &:= (20 - 4 + 1 - 58 - 37 + 456)^4 \\
 &:= (2 - 01 + 135 + 71 - 87 - 5)^5 & & & \mathbf{20435982904} := (-204 + 35 - 9 + 8 + 2904)^3 \\
 &:= (2 + 01 - 13 - 57 + 187 - 5)^5 & & & \mathbf{20503329553} := (-2 - 0503 + 3295 - 53)^3 \\
 &:= (201 - 13 - 57 - 18 + 7 - 5)^5 & & & \mathbf{20601435024} := (20 + 6 + 0143502 + 4)^2 \\
 &:= (201 - 1 - 35 + 7 + 18 - 75)^5 & & & \mathbf{20632736881} := (2 + 06 + 3 + 2 + 7 + 368 - 8 - 1)^4 \\
 &:= (2 + 0113 + 57 + 18 - 75)^5 & & & &:= (2 - 06 + 3 - 2 + 7 + 368 + 8 - 1)^4 \\
 &:= (2 + 0113 - 57 - 18 + 75)^5 & & & &:= (-2 - 06 + 3 + 2 + 7 + 368 + 8 - 1)^4 \\
 & \mathbf{20168071048} := (2016 + 8 + 0710 - 4 - 8)^3 & & & &:= (2 + 06 + 3 - 2 - 7 + 368 + 8 + 1)^4 \\
 & & & & &:= (-2 + 06 + 3 + 2 - 7 + 368 + 8 + 1)^4 \\
 & \mathbf{20212559424} := (202 + 1 + 2559 - 42 + 4)^3 & & & &:= (2 - 06 - 3 + 2 + 7 + 368 + 8 + 1)^4 \\
 & \mathbf{20279414583} := (2 + 02794 - 14 - 58 + 3)^3 & & & &:= (20 + 6 + 327 + 3 + 6 + 8 + 8 + 1)^4 \\
 & & & & &:= (20 + 6 + 3 - 2 - 7 + 368 - 8 - 1)^4 \\
 & \mathbf{20301732352} := (2030 - 1 + 732 - 35 + 2)^3 & & & &:= (20 - 6 - 3 + 2 + 7 + 368 - 8 - 1)^4
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} &:= (20 + 6 - 3 + 2 - 7 + 368 - 8 + 1)^4 &:= (-2 + 06 - 6 - 1 + 04 - 6 + 7 + 8 + 4)^9 \\ &:= (20 - 6 - 3 - 2 - 7 + 368 + 8 + 1)^4 &:= (-2 - 06 + 6 - 1 + 04 - 6 + 7 + 8 + 4)^9 \\ &:= (2 - 06 + 327 - 3 + 68 - 8 - 1)^4 &:= (-2 - 06 - 6 - 1 + 04 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 4)^9 \\ &:= (2 + 06 + 3 + 273 + 6 + 88 + 1)^4 &:= (20 + 6 + 6 - 1 - 04 + 6 - 7 - 8 - 4)^9 \\ &:= (2 + 06 + 3 + 273 + 6 + 8 + 81)^4 &:= (20 + 6 - 6 + 1 + 04 - 6 + 7 - 8 - 4)^9 \\ &:= (2 - 06 - 3 + 27 + 368 - 8 - 1)^4 &:= (20 - 6 + 6 + 1 + 04 - 6 + 7 - 8 - 4)^9 \\ &:= (206 + 3 + 2 + 73 + 6 + 88 + 1)^4 &:= (20 - 6 - 6 + 1 + 04 + 6 + 7 - 8 - 4)^9 \\ &:= (206 + 3 + 2 + 73 + 6 + 8 + 81)^4 &:= (20 + 6 - 6 - 1 + 04 - 6 - 7 + 8 - 4)^9 \\ &:= (20 + 63 + 273 + 6 + 8 + 8 + 1)^4 &:= (20 - 6 + 6 - 1 + 04 - 6 - 7 + 8 - 4)^9 \\ &:= (-20 - 6 + 327 + 3 + 68 + 8 - 1)^4 &:= (20 - 6 - 6 - 1 + 04 + 6 - 7 + 8 - 4)^9 \\ &:= (-20 - 6 + 327 - 3 - 6 + 88 - 1)^4 &:= (-20 + 6 + 6 + 1 + 04 + 6 + 7 + 8 - 4)^9 \\ &:= (20 + 6 + 3 + 273 + 68 + 8 + 1)^4 &:= (20 + 6 - 6 + 1 - 04 - 6 + 7 - 8 + 4)^9 \\ &:= (20 + 6 - 3 + 273 - 6 + 88 + 1)^4 &:= (20 - 6 + 6 + 1 - 04 - 6 + 7 - 8 + 4)^9 \\ &:= (20 - 6 - 3 + 273 + 6 + 88 + 1)^4 &:= (20 - 6 - 6 + 1 - 04 + 6 + 7 - 8 + 4)^9 \\ &:= (20 + 6 - 3 + 273 - 6 + 8 + 81)^4 &:= (20 + 6 - 6 - 1 - 04 - 6 - 7 + 8 + 4)^9 \\ &:= (20 - 6 - 3 + 273 + 6 + 8 + 81)^4 &:= (20 - 6 + 6 - 1 - 04 - 6 - 7 + 8 + 4)^9 \\ &:= (-20 - 6 + 3 + 27 + 368 + 8 - 1)^4 &:= (20 - 6 - 6 - 1 - 04 + 6 - 7 + 8 + 4)^9 \\ &:= (20 + 6 + 3 - 27 + 368 + 8 + 1)^4 &:= (-20 + 6 + 6 + 1 - 04 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 4)^9 \\ &:= (2 - 063 - 2 - 7 + 368 + 81)^4 &:= (-2 - 06 - 6 + 1 + 046 - 7 - 8 - 4)^9 \\ &:= (-2 - 063 + 2 - 7 + 368 + 81)^4 &:= (-20 - 6 + 61 + 04 - 6 - 7 - 8 - 4)^9 \\ &:= (20 + 63 + 2 + 7 + 368 - 81)^4 &:= (-20 - 6 + 61 - 04 - 6 - 7 - 8 + 4)^9 \\ &:= (20 - 6 - 327 + 3 + 688 + 1)^4 &:= (-20 + 6 - 6 - 1 + 046 - 7 - 8 + 4)^9 \\ &:= (2 + 063 + 27 + 368 - 81)^4 &:= (-20 - 6 + 6 - 1 + 046 - 7 - 8 + 4)^9 \\ &:= (20 - 63 + 273 + 68 + 81)^4 &:= (-2 + 066 + 1 - 046 + 7 - 8 - 4)^9 \\ &:= (20 - 63 - 27 + 368 + 81)^4 &:= (-2 + 066 - 1 - 046 - 7 + 8 - 4)^9 \\ \mathbf{20661046784} &:= (-2 + 06 + 6 - 1 + 04 + 6 + 7 - 8 - 4)^9 &:= (-2 + 066 + 1 + 04 - 67 + 8 + 4)^9 \\ &:= (2 + 06 + 6 + 1 - 04 + 6 - 7 + 8 - 4)^9 &:= (-2 - 066 - 1 + 04 + 67 + 8 + 4)^9 \\ &:= (2 + 06 + 6 - 1 - 04 - 6 + 7 + 8 - 4)^9 &:= (2 - 066 - 1 - 04 + 6 - 7 + 84)^9 \\ &:= (2 + 06 - 6 - 1 - 04 + 6 + 7 + 8 - 4)^9 &:= (-2 - 066 + 1 - 04 - 6 + 7 + 84)^9 \\ &:= (2 - 06 + 6 - 1 - 04 + 6 + 7 + 8 - 4)^9 &:= (-2 + 06 + 61 - 046 + 7 - 8 - 4)^9 \\ &:= (2 + 06 + 6 + 1 + 04 + 6 - 7 - 8 + 4)^9 &:= (2 - 06 + 61 - 046 + 7 - 8 + 4)^9 \\ &:= (2 + 06 + 6 - 1 + 04 - 6 + 7 - 8 + 4)^9 &:= (2 + 06 - 61 - 04 + 67 + 8 - 4)^9 \\ &:= (-2 + 06 + 6 - 1 - 04 + 6 + 7 - 8 + 4)^9 &:= (2 + 06 - 61 + 04 + 67 - 8 + 4)^9 \\ &:= (2 + 06 - 6 - 1 + 04 + 6 + 7 - 8 + 4)^9 &:= (-2 + 06 + 61 + 04 - 67 + 8 + 4)^9 \\ &:= (2 - 06 + 6 - 1 + 04 + 6 + 7 - 8 + 4)^9 &:= (-2 - 06 - 61 + 04 + 67 + 8 + 4)^9 \\ &:= (-2 + 06 + 6 + 1 + 04 - 6 - 7 + 8 + 4)^9 &:= (2 + 06 - 61 - 04 - 6 - 7 + 84)^9 \\ &:= (-2 + 06 - 6 + 1 + 04 + 6 - 7 + 8 + 4)^9 &:= (2 - 06 - 61 - 04 + 6 - 7 + 84)^9 \\ &:= (-2 - 06 + 6 + 1 + 04 + 6 - 7 + 8 + 4)^9 &:= (2 + 06 - 6 - 1 - 04 - 67 + 84)^9 \end{aligned}$$

$:= (2 - 06 + 6 - 1 - 04 - 67 + 84)^9$	$:= (-2 + 100 + 3 + 4 - 1 - 6 + 5 + 7 + 6)^5$
$:= (20 - 66 + 1 + 04 + 67 - 8 - 4)^9$	$:= (2 + 100 - 3 + 4 + 1 - 6 + 5 + 7 + 6)^5$
$:= (20 - 66 + 1 - 04 + 67 - 8 + 4)^9$	$:= (-2 + 100 - 3 - 4 + 1 + 6 + 5 + 7 + 6)^5$
$:= (-20 - 66 - 1 + 04 + 6 + 7 + 84)^9$	$:= (2 + 1 + 0034 + 1 + 65 + 7 + 6)^5$
$:= (20 + 6 - 61 + 046 + 7 - 8 + 4)^9$	$:= (2 + 1 + 003 + 41 + 6 + 57 + 6)^5$
$:= (-20 + 6 - 61 + 04 - 6 + 7 + 84)^9$	$:= (2 - 1 - 003 + 41 + 6 - 5 + 76)^5$
$:= (-20 - 6 - 61 + 04 + 6 + 7 + 84)^9$	$:= (2 + 1 - 003 + 41 - 6 + 5 + 76)^5$
$:= (-20 - 6 - 6 + 1 - 046 + 7 + 84)^9$	$:= (-2 - 1 + 003 + 41 - 6 + 5 + 76)^5$
$:= (-20 + 6 + 6 + 1 + 04 - 67 + 84)^9$	$:= (21 - 003 + 41 + 6 + 57 - 6)^5$
$:= (-2 - 066 + 10 + 4 - 6 + 78 - 4)^9$	$:= (21 - 003 + 41 - 6 + 57 + 6)^5$
$:= (2 + 066 + 10 + 4 + 6 - 78 + 4)^9$	$:= (2 + 100 - 3 + 41 - 6 - 5 - 7 - 6)^5$
$:= (-2 - 066 + 10 - 4 - 6 + 78 + 4)^9$	$:= (2 + 10 + 034 + 1 + 6 + 57 + 6)^5$
$:= (-2 - 066 - 10 + 4 + 6 + 78 + 4)^9$	$:= (-2 + 10 + 034 - 1 - 6 + 5 + 76)^5$
$:= (-2 + 06 - 6 + 104 - 6 - 78 - 4)^9$	$:= (2 + 10 - 03 + 41 + 65 + 7 - 6)^5$
$:= (-2 - 06 + 6 + 104 - 6 - 78 - 4)^9$	$:= (-2 + 10 + 03 + 41 + 65 - 7 + 6)^5$
$:= (-2 - 06 - 6 + 104 + 6 - 78 - 4)^9$	$:= (2 + 10 + 03 + 4 + 16 + 5 + 76)^5$
$:= (2 - 06 - 6 + 104 - 6 - 78 + 4)^9$	$:= (2 + 1 + 0034 + 16 + 57 + 6)^5$
$:= (-20 + 66 - 1 + 046 + 7 - 84)^9$	$:= (210 - 03 - 4 - 16 + 5 - 76)^5$
$:= (-20 - 6 + 61 - 04 + 67 - 84)^9$	$:= (2 + 100 + 34 - 16 - 5 + 7 - 6)^5$
$:= (20 + 6 + 6 + 10 + 46 - 78 + 4)^9$	$:= (2 + 100 + 3 - 41 + 65 - 7 - 6)^5$
$:= (-20 - 6 - 6 + 10 - 46 + 78 + 4)^9$	$:= (-2 + 10 - 034 + 1 + 65 + 76)^5$
$:= (-206 - 610 + 46 + 784)^9$	21047437081 $:= (2104 - 7 - 43 + 708 - 1)^3$
20683643625 $:= (2068 + 3 + 643 + 6 + 25)^3$	21071715921 $:= (210 + 7 + 171 + 5 - 9 - 2 - 1)^4$
$:= (2068 + 3 + 6 + 43 + 625)^3$	$:= (210 - 7 + 171 - 5 + 9 + 2 + 1)^4$
20706256936 $:= (2070 + 625 + 6 + 9 + 36)^3$	$:= (210 + 7 + 1 + 7 + 159 - 2 - 1)^4$
$:= (207 + 06 + 2569 - 36)^3$	$:= (210 + 7 - 1 + 7 + 159 - 2 + 1)^4$
20728886723 $:= (-207 + 2888 + 67 + 2 - 3)^3$	$:= (-210 + 7 + 1 - 7 - 1 + 592 - 1)^4$
20819570751 $:= (2081 + 9 + 5 + 707 - 51)^3$	$:= (-210 - 7 + 1 + 7 - 1 + 592 - 1)^4$
20842283008 $:= (-20 - 8 - 42 + 2830 - 08)^3$	$:= (-210 + 7 - 1 - 7 + 1 + 592 - 1)^4$
$:= (-208 - 42 + 2 - 8 + 3008)^3$	$:= (-210 - 7 - 1 + 7 + 1 + 592 - 1)^4$
20933297216 $:= (-209 + 3 - 3 + 2972 - 1 - 6)^3$	$:= (-210 + 7 - 1 - 7 - 1 + 592 + 1)^4$
$:= (-209 - 3 + 3 + 2972 - 1 - 6)^3$	$:= (-210 - 7 - 1 + 7 - 1 + 592 + 1)^4$
21003416576 $:= (21 + 003 + 4 + 1 + 6 + 5 + 76)^5$	$:= (210 + 7 + 171 + 5 + 9 - 21)^4$
$:= (-2 + 100 + 3 + 4 - 1 + 6 + 5 + 7 - 6)^5$	$:= (210 - 7 + 171 - 5 - 9 + 21)^4$
$:= (2 + 100 - 3 + 4 + 1 + 6 + 5 + 7 - 6)^5$	$:= (-210 + 71 - 71 + 592 - 1)^4$
$:= (-2 + 100 + 3 + 4 + 1 + 6 + 5 - 7 + 6)^5$	$:= (-210 - 71 + 71 + 592 - 1)^4$
$:= (2 + 100 - 3 + 4 - 1 + 6 - 5 + 7 + 6)^5$	21116119744 $:= (2111 + 611 - 9 + 7 + 44)^3$
$:= (2 + 100 + 3 - 4 + 1 + 6 - 5 + 7 + 6)^5$	21276960011 $:= (-2 - 1 + 2769 - 6 + 0011)^3$

$$\begin{aligned}
 \mathbf{21293813776} &:= (2+1-2+9+381-3+7-7-6)^4 & := (-2+1+293+81+3+7-7+6)^4 \\
 &:= (-2+1+2+9+381-3+7-7-6)^4 & := (-2+1+293+81+3-7+7+6)^4 \\
 &:= (-2-1-2+9+381+3+7-7-6)^4 & := (212+93+8+1-3+77-6)^4 \\
 &:= (2+1-2+9+381-3-7+7-6)^4 & := (212+93-8-1+3+77+6)^4 \\
 &:= (-2+1+2+9+381-3-7+7-6)^4 & := (212+93-8-1+3+7+76)^4 \\
 &:= (-2-1-2+9+381+3-7+7-6)^4 & := (212+9+3+8+137+7+6)^4 \\
 &:= (2+1+2-9+381-3+7+7-6)^4 & := (21-29+381+3+7-7+6)^4 \\
 &:= (2-1-2-9+381+3+7+7-6)^4 & := (21-29+381+3-7+7+6)^4 \\
 &:= (-2-1+2-9+381+3+7+7-6)^4 & := (-21+2-9+38+1+377-6)^4 \\
 &:= (2-1+2+9+381-3-7-7+6)^4 & := (-2-12-9+381+37-7-6)^4 \\
 &:= (-2+1-2+9+381+3-7-7+6)^4 & := (-2-1+293+8+13+77-6)^4 \\
 &:= (2+1-2-9+381+3+7-7+6)^4 & := (2-1+293-8+13+77+6)^4 \\
 &:= (-2+1+2-9+381+3+7-7+6)^4 & := (-2+1+293+8+13-7+76)^4 \\
 &:= (2+1-2-9+381+3-7+7+6)^4 & := (2-1+293-8+13+7+76)^4 \\
 &:= (-2+1+2-9+381+3-7+7+6)^4 & := (2+1-29+38-1+377-6)^4 \\
 &:= (21-2-9+381-3+7-7-6)^4 & := (2-1-29+38+1+377-6)^4 \\
 &:= (21-2-9+381-3-7+7-6)^4 & := (2-1-2+93-81+377-6)^4 \\
 &:= (-21+2+9+381+3+7+7-6)^4 & := (-2-1+2+93-81+377-6)^4 \\
 &:= (2+12+9-3-8-1+377-6)^4 & := (2-1-2-9-381-3+776)^4 \\
 &:= (-2+12-9+3+8-1+377-6)^4 & := (-2-1+2-9-381-3+776)^4 \\
 &:= (2+12-9-3+8+1+377-6)^4 & := (21+29-38-1+377-6)^4 \\
 &:= (2-12+9+3+8+1+377-6)^4 & := (21+2-93+81+377-6)^4 \\
 &:= (2+12-9+3-8-1+377+6)^4 & := (-21+2+9-381-3+776)^4 \\
 &:= (-2-12+9-3+8-1+377+6)^4 & := (2+129+38+137+76)^4 \\
 &:= (2+1+293+81-3+7+7-6)^4 & \\
 &:= (-2-1+293+81+3+7+7-6)^4 &
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 \mathbf{21465180100} &:= (2+146518-010+0)^2 & := (-21+5+54+58+2687)^3 \\
 \mathbf{21465473121} &:= (-2+146547-31-2-1)^2 & \mathbf{21573146884} := (-2+1+5-7-3+146884)^2 \\
 \mathbf{21466059169} &:= (2+146605-91+6-9)^2 & := (2+1-5-7+3+146884)^2 \\
 \mathbf{21508145541} &:= (2150+81+4+5+541)^3 & := (-21+5+7+3+146884)^2 \\
 \mathbf{21517662721} &:= (215+176-6+2-7+2+1)^4 & \mathbf{21577826304} := (2157+7-8+2+630-4)^3 \\
 &:= (2+1+517-66+2-72-1)^4 & := (2+157+7-8+2630-4)^3 \\
 &:= (2-1+517-66+2-72+1)^4 & \mathbf{21624363656} := (2162-4+3+636-5-6)^3 \\
 &:= (-21+51+76+6+272-1)^4 & := (-2-1-6+2436+365-6)^3 \\
 \mathbf{21531355768} &:= (2153+1+3+557+68)^3 & \mathbf{21743271936} := (-21-7+432-7-1-9+3-6)^4 \\
 &:= (215+3135-576+8)^3 & := (217+4+3+2+71+93-6)^4 \\
 \mathbf{21554582687} &:= (-21+55+4+58+2687)^3 & := (217-4+3-2+71+93+6)^4
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 &:= (-2 - 17 + 432 - 7 - 19 + 3 - 6)^4 \\
 &:= (2 - 17 + 432 - 7 + 1 + 9 - 36)^4 \\
 &:= (-2 + 17 - 4 + 327 + 1 + 9 + 36)^4 \\
 &:= (2 + 17 + 4 + 3 + 271 + 93 - 6)^4 \\
 &:= (-2 + 17 - 4 + 3 + 271 + 93 + 6)^4 \\
 &:= (-2 + 1 + 74 + 327 - 19 - 3 + 6)^4 \\
 &:= (-2 - 1 + 74 - 3 + 271 + 9 + 36)^4 \\
 &:= (2 + 1 - 7 + 432 - 71 - 9 + 36)^4 \\
 &:= (-2 + 1 + 7 - 4 + 327 + 19 + 36)^4 \\
 &:= (217 + 4 + 3 - 27 + 193 - 6)^4 \\
 &:= (21 - 7 + 432 - 7 - 19 - 36)^4 \\
 &:= (-2 + 174 + 32 - 7 + 193 - 6)^4 \\
 &:= (-2 + 1 + 743 - 271 - 93 + 6)^4 \\
 \mathbf{21904993592} &:= (-2 + 1904 + 993 - 5 - 92)^3 \\
 \mathbf{21924480357} &:= (2 + 1 + 9 + 2 + 4 + 4 + 80 + 3 + 5 + 7)^5 \\
 &:= (21 + 9 - 2 + 4 + 4 + 80 + 3 + 5 - 7)^5 \\
 &:= (21 + 9 + 2 + 4 - 4 + 80 + 3 - 5 + 7)^5 \\
 &:= (21 + 9 + 2 - 4 + 4 + 80 + 3 - 5 + 7)^5 \\
 &:= (21 + 9 - 2 + 4 - 4 + 80 - 3 + 5 + 7)^5 \\
 &:= (21 + 9 - 2 - 4 + 4 + 80 - 3 + 5 + 7)^5 \\
 &:= (21 - 9 + 2 + 4 + 4 + 80 + 3 + 5 + 7)^5 \\
 &:= (-2 - 1 + 92 + 4 + 4 - 8 + 035 - 7)^5 \\
 &:= (-2 - 1 + 92 - 4 - 4 + 8 + 035 - 7)^5 \\
 &:= (-2 + 1 + 92 - 4 - 4 - 8 + 035 + 7)^5 \\
 &:= (-2 + 1 + 9 + 24 + 4 + 80 + 3 + 5 - 7)^5 \\
 &:= (2 - 1 + 9 + 24 + 4 + 80 - 3 - 5 + 7)^5 \\
 &:= (2 + 1 + 9 + 24 - 4 + 80 + 3 - 5 + 7)^5 \\
 &:= (-2 + 1 + 9 + 24 - 4 + 80 - 3 + 5 + 7)^5 \\
 &:= (2 + 1 - 9 + 24 + 4 + 80 + 3 + 5 + 7)^5 \\
 &:= (2 - 1 + 9 - 2 + 44 + 80 - 3 - 5 - 7)^5 \\
 &:= (-2 - 1 + 9 + 2 + 44 + 80 - 3 - 5 - 7)^5 \\
 &:= (2 + 1 - 9 - 2 + 44 + 80 + 3 + 5 - 7)^5 \\
 &:= (-2 + 1 - 9 + 2 + 44 + 80 + 3 + 5 - 7)^5 \\
 &:= (2 - 1 - 9 + 2 + 44 + 80 - 3 - 5 + 7)^5 \\
 &:= (-2 + 1 - 9 - 2 + 44 + 80 + 3 - 5 + 7)^5 \\
 &:= (-21 + 92 + 4 - 4 - 8 - 03 + 57)^5 \\
 &:= (-21 + 92 - 4 + 4 - 8 - 03 + 57)^5 \\
 &:= (21 + 9 + 24 + 48 + 03 + 5 + 7)^5
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 &:= (21 - 9 + 24 - 4 + 80 + 3 - 5 + 7)^5 \\
 &:= (2 + 192 + 4 + 4 - 80 - 3 + 5 - 7)^5 \\
 &:= (-2 + 192 + 4 + 4 - 80 - 3 - 5 + 7)^5 \\
 &:= (-2 + 192 - 4 - 4 - 80 + 3 + 5 + 7)^5 \\
 &:= (2 + 19 + 24 + 4 + 8 + 03 + 57)^5 \\
 &:= (2 + 19 + 2 + 44 + 8 + 035 + 7)^5 \\
 &:= (2 + 19 + 2 + 4 + 48 + 035 + 7)^5 \\
 &:= (2 + 19 - 2 - 4 + 48 - 03 + 57)^5 \\
 &:= (-2 + 19 + 2 - 4 + 48 - 03 + 57)^5 \\
 &:= (2 - 19 + 2 - 4 - 4 + 80 + 3 + 57)^5 \\
 &:= (-2 - 19 - 2 + 4 - 4 + 80 + 3 + 57)^5 \\
 &:= (-2 - 19 - 2 - 4 + 4 + 80 + 3 + 57)^5 \\
 &:= (2 - 1 + 92 + 44 + 8 - 035 + 7)^5 \\
 &:= (2 - 1 + 92 - 44 + 8 + 03 + 57)^5 \\
 &:= (2 - 1 + 92 + 4 + 48 - 035 + 7)^5 \\
 &:= (-2 - 1 + 92 + 4 + 4 + 80 - 3 - 57)^5 \\
 &:= (-2 + 1 + 92 + 4 - 4 + 80 + 3 - 57)^5 \\
 &:= (-2 + 1 + 92 - 4 + 4 + 80 + 3 - 57)^5 \\
 &:= (219 + 2 + 4 - 48 - 03 - 57)^5 \\
 &:= (219 - 2 + 4 + 4 - 80 - 35 + 7)^5 \\
 &:= (-21 + 92 + 4 + 4 + 80 - 35 - 7)^5 \\
 &:= (-2 + 19 + 24 + 48 + 035 - 7)^5 \\
 &:= (2 - 1 + 92 + 44 - 80 + 3 + 57)^5 \\
 &:= (2 + 1 + 9 - 244 - 8 + 0357)^5 \\
 &:= (2 - 1 - 9 - 2 + 4 + 480 - 357)^5 \\
 &:= (-2 - 1 - 9 + 2 + 4 + 480 - 357)^5 \\
 &:= (219 + 24 - 4 - 80 - 35 - 7)^5 \\
 &:= (21 - 9 - 244 - 8 + 0357)^5 \\
 &:= (-21 + 9 + 2 + 4 + 480 - 357)^5 \\
 &:= (-21 - 9 + 24 + 480 - 357)^5 \\
 \mathbf{21928488399} &:= (2 + 1928 + 4 + 883 - 9 - 9)^3 \\
 \mathbf{21948126201} &:= (21948 + 126201)^2 \\
 \mathbf{21970650625} &:= (-21 - 97 - 06 + 506 - 2 + 5)^4 \\
 &:= (219 + 70 + 65 + 06 + 25)^4 \\
 \mathbf{21975528401} &:= (-2 - 19 - 7 - 5 - 5 + 2840 - 1)^3 \\
 &:= (2 - 1 + 9 + 7 - 55 + 2840 - 1)^3 \\
 &:= (-2 + 1 + 9 + 7 - 55 + 2840 + 1)^3 \\
 &:= (21 + 9 - 75 + 5 + 2840 + 1)^3
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{21999073608} &:= (2199 - 9 + 07 - 3 + 608)^3 &:= (2 + 2 - 1 - 6 + 43 + 6 - 1 + 1 - 2 + 9)^6 \\ \mathbf{22093422616} &:= (220 + 9 + 3 - 42 + 2616)^3 &:= (2 - 2 + 1 + 6 + 43 - 6 + 1 + 1 - 2 + 9)^6 \\ &:= (2209 + 342 + 261 - 6)^3 &:= (-2 + 2 + 1 + 6 + 43 - 6 + 1 + 1 - 2 + 9)^6 \\ \mathbf{22117051943} &:= (2211 + 70 + 519 + 4 + 3)^3 &:= (2 - 2 + 1 - 6 + 43 + 6 + 1 + 1 - 2 + 9)^6 \\ \mathbf{22164361129} &:= (22 + 1 + 6 + 4 + 3 + 6 + 1 - 1 + 2 + 9)^6 &:= (-2 + 2 + 1 - 6 + 43 + 6 + 1 + 1 - 2 + 9)^6 \\ &:= (22 + 1 + 6 + 4 + 3 + 6 - 1 + 1 + 2 + 9)^6 &:= (2 - 2 + 1 + 6 + 43 - 6 - 1 - 1 + 2 + 9)^6 \\ &:= (22 - 1 + 6 + 4 + 3 + 6 + 1 + 1 + 2 + 9)^6 &:= (-2 + 2 + 1 + 6 + 43 - 6 - 1 - 1 + 2 + 9)^6 \\ &:= (2 + 21 + 6 + 4 + 3 + 6 + 1 - 1 + 2 + 9)^6 &:= (2 - 2 + 1 - 6 + 43 + 6 - 1 - 1 + 2 + 9)^6 \\ &:= (2 + 21 + 6 + 4 + 3 + 6 - 1 + 1 + 2 + 9)^6 &:= (-2 + 2 + 1 - 6 + 43 + 6 - 1 - 1 + 2 + 9)^6 \\ &:= (2 + 2 + 1 + 64 + 3 - 6 - 1 - 1 - 2 - 9)^6 &:= (2 - 2 - 1 + 6 + 43 - 6 + 1 - 1 + 2 + 9)^6 \\ &:= (2 - 2 - 1 + 64 - 3 + 6 - 1 - 1 - 2 - 9)^6 &:= (-2 + 2 - 1 + 6 + 43 - 6 + 1 - 1 + 2 + 9)^6 \\ &:= (-2 + 2 - 1 + 64 - 3 + 6 - 1 - 1 - 2 - 9)^6 &:= (2 - 2 - 1 - 6 + 43 + 6 + 1 - 1 + 2 + 9)^6 \\ &:= (2 + 2 - 1 + 64 + 3 - 6 + 1 - 1 - 2 - 9)^6 &:= (-2 + 2 - 1 - 6 + 43 + 6 + 1 - 1 + 2 + 9)^6 \\ &:= (-2 - 2 + 1 + 64 - 3 + 6 + 1 - 1 - 2 - 9)^6 &:= (2 - 2 - 1 + 6 + 43 - 6 - 1 + 1 + 2 + 9)^6 \\ &:= (2 + 2 - 1 + 64 + 3 - 6 - 1 + 1 - 2 - 9)^6 &:= (-2 + 2 - 1 + 6 + 43 - 6 - 1 + 1 + 2 + 9)^6 \\ &:= (-2 - 2 + 1 + 64 - 3 + 6 - 1 + 1 - 2 - 9)^6 &:= (2 - 2 - 1 - 6 + 43 + 6 - 1 + 1 + 2 + 9)^6 \\ &:= (2 - 2 + 1 + 64 + 3 - 6 + 1 + 1 - 2 - 9)^6 &:= (-2 + 2 - 1 - 6 + 43 + 6 - 1 + 1 + 2 + 9)^6 \\ &:= (-2 - 2 - 1 + 64 - 3 + 6 + 1 + 1 - 2 - 9)^6 &:= (2 - 2 - 1 + 6 + 43 - 6 + 1 + 1 + 2 + 9)^6 \\ &:= (2 - 2 + 1 + 64 + 3 - 6 - 1 - 1 + 2 - 9)^6 &:= (-2 - 2 + 1 + 6 + 43 - 6 + 1 + 1 + 2 + 9)^6 \\ &:= (-2 + 2 + 1 + 64 + 3 - 6 - 1 - 1 + 2 - 9)^6 &:= (2 + 2 + 1 + 6 - 4 - 3 + 61 - 1 - 2 - 9)^6 \\ &:= (-2 - 2 - 1 + 64 - 3 + 6 - 1 - 1 + 2 - 9)^6 &:= (-2 - 2 + 1 + 6 + 4 - 3 + 61 - 1 - 2 - 9)^6 \\ &:= (2 + 2 + 1 + 64 - 3 - 6 + 1 - 1 + 2 - 9)^6 &:= (2 - 2 - 1 + 6 - 4 + 3 + 61 - 1 - 2 - 9)^6 \\ &:= (2 - 2 - 1 + 64 + 3 - 6 + 1 - 1 + 2 - 9)^6 &:= (-2 + 2 - 1 + 6 - 4 + 3 + 61 - 1 - 2 - 9)^6 \\ &:= (-2 + 2 - 1 + 64 + 3 - 6 + 1 - 1 + 2 - 9)^6 &:= (2 + 2 - 1 - 6 + 4 + 3 + 61 - 1 - 2 - 9)^6 \\ &:= (2 + 2 + 1 + 64 - 3 - 6 - 1 + 1 + 2 - 9)^6 &:= (-2 - 2 - 1 + 6 + 4 - 3 + 61 + 1 - 2 - 9)^6 \\ &:= (2 - 2 - 1 + 64 + 3 - 6 - 1 + 1 + 2 - 9)^6 &:= (-2 - 2 + 1 + 6 - 4 + 3 + 61 + 1 - 2 - 9)^6 \\ &:= (-2 + 2 - 1 + 64 + 3 - 6 - 1 + 1 + 2 - 9)^6 &:= (2 - 2 + 1 - 6 + 4 + 3 + 61 + 1 - 2 - 9)^6 \\ &:= (2 + 2 - 1 + 64 - 3 - 6 + 1 + 1 + 2 - 9)^6 &:= (-2 + 2 + 1 - 6 + 4 + 3 + 61 + 1 - 2 - 9)^6 \\ &:= (-2 - 2 + 1 + 64 + 3 - 6 + 1 + 1 + 2 - 9)^6 &:= (2 - 2 + 1 + 6 - 4 - 3 + 61 - 1 + 2 - 9)^6 \\ &:= (2 + 2 + 1 + 6 + 43 + 6 + 1 - 1 + 2 - 9)^6 &:= (-2 + 2 + 1 + 6 - 4 - 3 + 61 - 1 + 2 - 9)^6 \\ &:= (2 + 2 + 1 + 6 + 43 + 6 - 1 + 1 + 2 - 9)^6 &:= (2 + 2 + 1 - 6 + 4 - 3 + 61 - 1 + 2 - 9)^6 \\ &:= (2 + 2 - 1 + 6 + 43 + 6 + 1 + 1 + 2 - 9)^6 &:= (-2 - 2 - 1 + 6 - 4 + 3 + 61 - 1 + 2 - 9)^6 \\ &:= (2 + 2 + 1 + 6 + 43 - 6 - 1 - 1 - 2 + 9)^6 &:= (2 - 2 - 1 - 6 + 4 + 3 + 61 - 1 + 2 - 9)^6 \\ &:= (2 + 2 + 1 - 6 + 43 + 6 - 1 - 1 - 2 + 9)^6 &:= (-2 + 2 - 1 - 6 + 4 + 3 + 61 - 1 + 2 - 9)^6 \\ &:= (2 + 2 - 1 + 6 + 43 - 6 + 1 - 1 - 2 + 9)^6 &:= (2 - 2 - 1 + 6 - 4 - 3 + 61 + 1 + 2 - 9)^6 \\ &:= (2 + 2 - 1 - 6 + 43 + 6 + 1 - 1 - 2 + 9)^6 &:= (-2 + 2 - 1 + 6 - 4 - 3 + 61 + 1 + 2 - 9)^6 \\ &:= (2 + 2 - 1 + 6 + 43 - 6 - 1 + 1 - 2 + 9)^6 &:= (2 + 2 - 1 - 6 + 4 - 3 + 61 + 1 + 2 - 9)^6 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} &:= (2+2+1-6-4+3+61+1+2-9)^6 &:= (2-21+64+3-6-1+1+2+9)^6 \\ &:= (-2-2+1-6+4+3+61+1+2-9)^6 &:= (2+21+6+43-6-1-1-2-9)^6 \\ &:= (2-2-1-6-4-3+61-1-2+9)^6 &:= (2+21-6+43+6-1-1-2-9)^6 \\ &:= (-2+2-1-6-4-3+61-1-2+9)^6 &:= (-2+21+6+43-6+1+1-2-9)^6 \\ &:= (-2-2+1-6-4-3+61+1-2+9)^6 &:= (-2+21-6+43+6+1+1-2-9)^6 \\ &:= (-2-2-1-6-4-3+61-1+2+9)^6 &:= (-2+21+6+43-6-1-1+2-9)^6 \\ &:= (2+2+1+6+4+3+6+1-1+29)^6 &:= (-2+21-6+43+6-1-1+2-9)^6 \\ &:= (2+2+1+6+4+3+6-1+1+29)^6 &:= (2-21+6-4+3+61-1-2+9)^6 \\ &:= (2+2-1+6+4+3+6+1+1+29)^6 &:= (-2-21+6+4-3+61+1-2+9)^6 \\ &:= (-22+1+64-3+6+1-1-2+9)^6 &:= (-2-21+6-4+3+61-1+2+9)^6 \\ &:= (-22+1+64-3+6-1+1-2+9)^6 &:= (2-21-6+4+3+61-1+2+9)^6 \\ &:= (-22-1+64-3+6+1+1-2+9)^6 &:= (2-21+6-4-3+61+1+2+9)^6 \\ &:= (-22-1+64-3+6-1-1+2+9)^6 &:= (-2+21+6+4+3-6-1-1+29)^6 \\ &:= (-22+1+64+3-6+1+1+2+9)^6 &:= (-2+21-6+4+3+6-1-1+29)^6 \\ &:= (22+1+6+43-6-1-1-2-9)^6 &:= (2+21+6+4-3-6+1-1+29)^6 \\ &:= (22+1-6+43+6-1-1-2-9)^6 &:= (-2+21+6-4-3+6+1-1+29)^6 \\ &:= (22-1+6+43-6+1-1-2-9)^6 &:= (2+21-6+4-3+6+1-1+29)^6 \\ &:= (22-1-6+43+6+1-1-2-9)^6 &:= (2+21+6+4-3-6-1+1+29)^6 \\ &:= (22-1+6+43-6-1+1-2-9)^6 &:= (-2+21+6-4-3+6-1+1+29)^6 \\ &:= (22-1-6+43+6-1+1-2-9)^6 &:= (2+21-6+4-3+6-1+1+29)^6 \\ &:= (-22+1+6+4-3+61-1-2+9)^6 &:= (2+21+6-4+3-6+1+1+29)^6 \\ &:= (-22-1+6+4-3+61+1-2+9)^6 &:= (2+21-6-4+3+6+1+1+29)^6 \\ &:= (-22+1+6-4+3+61+1-2+9)^6 &:= (2+2+16+4+36+1-1+2-9)^6 \\ &:= (-22-1+6-4+3+61-1+2+9)^6 &:= (2+2+16+4+36-1+1+2-9)^6 \\ &:= (-22+1-6+4+3+61+1+2+9)^6 &:= (2-2+16-4+36-1-1-2+9)^6 \\ &:= (22-1+6-4-3+6-1-1+29)^6 &:= (-2+2+16-4+36-1-1-2+9)^6 \\ &:= (22+1+6+4-3-6+1-1+29)^6 &:= (-2-2+16-4+36+1+1-2+9)^6 \\ &:= (22+1-6+4-3+6+1-1+29)^6 &:= (-2-2+16-4+36-1-1+2+9)^6 \\ &:= (22+1+6+4-3-6-1+1+29)^6 &:= (2+2+16+4+3+6-1+12+9)^6 \\ &:= (22+1-6+4-3+6-1+1+29)^6 &:= (-2-2-1-6+43-6-1-1+29)^6 \\ &:= (22-1+6+4-3-6+1+1+29)^6 &:= (2+2-1+6+4+36+11+2-9)^6 \\ &:= (22+1+6-4+3-6+1+1+29)^6 &:= (-2-2+1+6-4+36+11-2+9)^6 \\ &:= (22-1-6+4-3+6+1+1+29)^6 &:= (2-2+1-6+4+36+11-2+9)^6 \\ &:= (22+1-6-4+3+6+1+1+29)^6 &:= (-2+2+1-6+4+36+11-2+9)^6 \\ &:= (2-21+64-3+6-1-1-2+9)^6 &:= (2+2+1-6-4+36+11+2+9)^6 \\ &:= (-2-21+64-3+6+1+1-2+9)^6 &:= (-2-2+1-6+4+36+11+2+9)^6 \\ &:= (-2-21+64-3+6-1-1+2+9)^6 &:= (2+2+1+6+4+36-1+12-9)^6 \\ &:= (2-21+64+3-6+1-1+2+9)^6 &:= (2+2-1+6+4+36+1+12-9)^6 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} & := (-2-2-1+6-4+36-1+12+9)^6 & := (2+21-6+4+36-11-2+9)^6 \\ & := (2-2-1-6+4+36-1+12+9)^6 & := (-2+21-6+4+36-11+2+9)^6 \\ & := (-2+2-1-6+4+36-1+12+9)^6 & := (2+21-6-4+36+1+12-9)^6 \\ & := (2+2+1-6-4+36+1+12+9)^6 & := (-2+21+6-4+36-1-12+9)^6 \\ & := (-2-2+1-6+4+36+1+12+9)^6 & := (2+21-6+4+36-1-12+9)^6 \\ & := (22-16+4+36+1-1-2+9)^6 & := (2+21+6-4-3+61-1-29)^6 \\ & := (22-16+4+36-1+1-2+9)^6 & := (-2+21-6+4+3+61+1-29)^6 \\ & := (22+16-4+3-6+11+2+9)^6 & := (-2-21-6-4-3+61-1+29)^6 \\ & := (22+16+4+3+6-1+12-9)^6 & := (2-2+16+43-6+11-2-9)^6 \\ & := (22+16+4-3-6-1+12+9)^6 & := (-2+2+16+43-6+11-2-9)^6 \\ & := (22+16-4+3-6+1+12+9)^6 & := (-2-2+16+43-6+11+2-9)^6 \\ & := (22+1+64+3-6-1-1-29)^6 & := (2+2+16+43-6-11-2+9)^6 \\ & := (22-1+64+3-6+1-1-29)^6 & := (2-2+16+43-6-11+2+9)^6 \\ & := (22-1+64+3-6-1+1-29)^6 & := (-2+2+16+43-6-11+2+9)^6 \\ & := (22+1+6-43+61-1-2+9)^6 & := (-2-2+16+43-6+1+12-9)^6 \\ & := (22-1+6-43+61+1-2+9)^6 & := (2+2+16+43-6-1-12+9)^6 \\ & := (-22+1+6+43-6+1+1+29)^6 & := (2-2-16+43+6-1+12+9)^6 \\ & := (-22+1-6+43+6+1+1+29)^6 & := (-2+2-16+43+6-1+12+9)^6 \\ & := (22+1-6-4+36+11+2-9)^6 & := (2-2-16+4+36+1-1+29)^6 \\ & := (22+1-6+4+36-11-2+9)^6 & := (-2+2-16+4+36+1-1+29)^6 \\ & := (22+1-6-4+36+1+12-9)^6 & := (2-2-16+4+36-1+1+29)^6 \\ & := (22+1-6+4+36-1-12+9)^6 & := (-2+2-16+4+36-1+1+29)^6 \\ & := (22-1-6+4+36+1-12+9)^6 & := (2+2+16-4-3+61-12-9)^6 \\ & := (22+1+6-4-3+61-1-29)^6 & := (-2-2+16+4-3+61-12-9)^6 \\ & := (22-1-6+4+3+61-1-29)^6 & := (2+2-16+4-3+61+12-9)^6 \\ & := (22-1+6-4-3+61+1-29)^6 & := (2+2-16+4+3+61-12+9)^6 \\ & := (-22-1-6-4-3+61-1+29)^6 & := (2+2+16-4+3-6+11+29)^6 \\ & := (2+21+64+3-6-1-1-29)^6 & := (-2-2+16+4+3-6+11+29)^6 \\ & := (-2+21+64+3-6+1+1-29)^6 & := (2+2-1+64-36+11+2+9)^6 \\ & := (2+21+6-43+61-1-2+9)^6 & := (2+2+1+64-36-1+12+9)^6 \\ & := (-2+21+6-43+61-1+2+9)^6 & := (2+2-1+64-36+1+12+9)^6 \\ & := (2-21+6+43-6+1-1+29)^6 & := (2+2+1-64+3+6+112-9)^6 \\ & := (2-21-6+43+6+1-1+29)^6 & := (2+2+1-64-3-6+112+9)^6 \\ & := (2-21+6+43-6-1+1+29)^6 & := (2-2-1-64+3-6+112+9)^6 \\ & := (2-21-6+43+6-1+1+29)^6 & := (-2+2-1-64+3-6+112+9)^6 \\ & := (-2+21-6+4+36+11-2-9)^6 & := (2-2+1+6-43+61-1+29)^6 \\ & := (2+21-6-4+36+11+2-9)^6 & := (-2+2+1+6-43+61-1+29)^6 \\ & := (-2+21+6-4+36-11-2+9)^6 & := (2-2-1+6-43+61+1+29)^6 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 & := (-2+2-1+6-43+61+1+29)^6 & & := (2+2164+3+611+29)^3 \\
 & := (2+2+1-6-43-6+112-9)^6 & & := (221+64-361+129)^6 \\
 & := (-2-2+1+6-4+36-11+29)^6 & & \mathbf{22199808016} := (221+9-9+80+80-1+6)^4 \\
 & := (2-2+1-6+4+36-11+29)^6 & & := (221-9+9+80+80-1+6)^4 \\
 & := (-2+2+1-6+4+36-11+29)^6 & & := (22+199+80+80-1+6)^4 \\
 & := (22+16+43-6-11-2-9)^6 & & \mathbf{22211737731} := (2-2+2117-37+731)^3 \\
 & := (-22+16+43-6+11+2+9)^6 & & := (-2+2+2117-37+731)^3 \\
 & := (22+16+43-6-1-12-9)^6 & & \mathbf{22282929144} := (-2-2+2829-2+9-14-4)^3 \\
 & := (22-16+43+6+1-12+9)^6 & & := (-22+2829-2-9+14+4)^3 \\
 & := (-22+16+43-6+1+12+9)^6 & & := (2+2+2829-29+14-4)^3 \\
 & := (-22+16-4+36-1-1+29)^6 & & := (-2-2+2829-29+14+4)^3 \\
 & := (22-16+4+3+61-12-9)^6 & & \mathbf{22354272513} := (2+2+3542-725-1-3)^3 \\
 & := (-22+16+4-3+61-12+9)^6 & & := (-2-2+3542-725+1+3)^3 \\
 & := (22-16+4-3+6+11+29)^6 & & := (22+3+54+2725+13)^3 \\
 & := (22-1+64-36+11+2-9)^6 & & := (2+23+54+2725+13)^3 \\
 & := (22+1+64-36-1+12-9)^6 & & := (223+54+27+2513)^3 \\
 & := (22-1+64-36+1+12-9)^6 & & \mathbf{22430753361} := (2+2+4+3+07+5+3+361)^4 \\
 & := (22+1+64-3-61+1+29)^6 & & := (22-4+3+07-5+3+361)^4 \\
 & := (22+1-64+3+61+1+29)^6 & & := (-2+24+3-07+5+3+361)^4 \\
 & := (22+1-64-3-6+112-9)^6 & & := (2-2+430+7+5+3+3-61)^4 \\
 & := (-22+1-6+4+36+11+29)^6 & & := (-2+2+430+7+5+3+3-61)^4 \\
 & := (2+21+64-36-1+12-9)^6 & & := (2+2+4+307+5+3+3+61)^4 \\
 & := (-2+21+64+3-61-1+29)^6 & & := (2+2+4+30+7+5+336+1)^4 \\
 & := (2+21+64-3-61+1+29)^6 & & := (22+430+7-5-3-3-61)^4 \\
 & := (2+21-64+3+61+1+29)^6 & & := (-22+43+07-5+3+361)^4 \\
 & := (2+21-64-3-6+112-9)^6 & & := (22-4+307-5+3+3+61)^4 \\
 & := (2-21+6-43+6+112-9)^6 & & := (22-4+30+7-5+336+1)^4 \\
 & := (2-2-16+4-3-61+129)^6 & & := (-22-4+3+075+336-1)^4 \\
 & := (-2+2-16+4-3-61+129)^6 & & := (2+243+075+3+3+61)^4 \\
 & := (2216-4-3+611-2-9)^3 & & := (-2+24+30-7+5+336+1)^4 \\
 & := (221-6+4-36-1-129)^6 & & := (-2-24+3+075+336-1)^4 \\
 & := (22+164+3-6-1-129)^6 & & := (2-24-3+075+336+1)^4 \\
 & := (22+16-43+61-12+9)^6 & & := (2+2+430-75+33-6+1)^4 \\
 & := (-22-16-43+6-1+129)^6 & & := (2-2+430-75-3+36-1)^4 \\
 & := (22+1-64-36+1+129)^6 & & := (-2+2+430-75-3+36-1)^4 \\
 & := (2+216-43+6+1-129)^6 & & := (-2-2-4+307+53+36-1)^4 \\
 & := (-2+216-4-36-112-9)^6 & & := (2-2-4-30+7+53+361)^4 \\
 & := (2+21-64-36+1+129)^6 & & := (-2+2-4-30+7+53+361)^4
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 & := (-2 - 2 - 4 + 3 + 0753 - 361)^4 & & := (-2 - 2 + 66 + 349 - 59 + 36)^4 \\
 & := (2 - 24 - 30 + 75 + 3 + 361)^4 & & := (2 + 2 + 6 - 63 - 495 + 936)^4 \\
 & := (2 - 2 - 430 + 753 + 3 + 61)^4 & & \mathbf{22713274368} := (-2 + 27 - 1 - 3 + 2743 + 68)^3 \\
 & := (-2 + 2 - 430 + 753 + 3 + 61)^4 & & \mathbf{22761429704} := (2 + 2761 + 4 + 2 - 9 + 70 + 4)^3 \\
 & := (2 + 2 + 430 - 75 - 33 + 61)^4 & & \mathbf{22785532875} := (-22 - 7 - 8 + 5 - 5 - 3 + 2875)^3 \\
 \mathbf{22449633661} & := (-2 + 2449 + 6 + 3 + 366 - 1)^3 & & := (-22 - 7 - 8 - 5 + 5 - 3 + 2875)^3 \\
 & := (2 + 2449 + 6 - 3 + 366 + 1)^3 & & := (2 + 2785 + 5 + 3 + 28 + 7 + 5)^3 \\
 & := (2244 + 9 + 633 - 66 + 1)^3 & & := (-2 - 27 - 8 + 5 - 5 - 3 + 2875)^3 \\
 \mathbf{22521332224} & := (2 + 2521 + 3 + 322 - 24)^3 & & := (-2 - 27 - 8 - 5 + 5 - 3 + 2875)^3 \\
 \mathbf{22545265625} & := (2 + 2545 + 265 + 6 + 2 + 5)^3 & & := (2 - 27 - 8 - 5 - 5 + 3 + 2875)^3 \\
 \mathbf{22569215976} & := (22 + 569 + 2159 + 76)^3 & & := (2278 + 553 - 2 + 8 - 7 + 5)^3 \\
 \mathbf{22615046689} & := (2 - 2 + 6 + 150466 - 89)^2 & & := (2278 + 5 + 532 + 8 + 7 + 5)^3 \\
 & := (-2 + 2 + 6 + 150466 - 89)^2 & & \mathbf{22809653056} := (2 + 2809 + 6 + 5 + 3 + 05 + 6)^3 \\
 & & & := (2280 + 9 + 6 + 530 + 5 + 6)^3 \\
 \mathbf{22663495936} & := (2 + 2 + 6 + 6 + 349 + 5 + 9 + 3 + 6)^4 & & := (-228 + 09 - 6 + 5 + 3056)^3 \\
 & := (22 + 6 + 6 + 349 + 5 + 9 - 3 - 6)^4 & & := (2 + 2809 - 6 + 5 - 30 + 56)^3 \\
 & := (22 + 6 - 6 + 349 + 5 + 9 - 3 + 6)^4 & & \mathbf{22833790253} := (-2 + 2833 + 7 + 9 - 02 - 5 - 3)^3 \\
 & := (22 - 6 + 6 + 349 + 5 + 9 - 3 + 6)^4 & & := (2 + 2833 - 7 + 9 - 02 + 5 - 3)^3 \\
 & := (22 + 6 + 6 + 349 + 5 - 9 + 3 + 6)^4 & & := (2 + 2833 + 7 - 9 + 02 + 5 - 3)^3 \\
 & := (2 + 266 + 3 + 4 + 95 + 9 + 3 + 6)^4 & & := (-2 + 2833 - 7 + 9 + 02 + 5 - 3)^3 \\
 & := (2 + 266 + 3 + 4 + 9 + 5 + 93 + 6)^4 & & := (2 + 2833 - 7 + 9 + 02 - 5 + 3)^3 \\
 & := (2 + 26 + 6 + 349 + 5 + 9 - 3 - 6)^4 & & := (-2 + 2833 - 7 - 9 + 025 - 3)^3 \\
 & := (2 + 26 - 6 + 349 + 5 + 9 - 3 + 6)^4 & & \mathbf{22877577568} := (-2 - 2 + 87 + 7 + 5 + 7 + 7 - 5 + 6 + 8)^5 \\
 & := (2 + 26 + 6 + 349 + 5 - 9 + 3 + 6)^4 & & := (2 - 2 + 87 + 7 + 5 + 7 - 7 + 5 + 6 + 8)^5 \\
 & := (-2 - 2 + 66 + 349 - 5 - 9 - 3 - 6)^4 & & := (-2 + 2 + 87 + 7 + 5 + 7 - 7 + 5 + 6 + 8)^5 \\
 & := (-226 + 634 - 9 - 5 - 9 - 3 + 6)^4 & & := (2 - 2 + 87 + 7 + 5 - 7 + 7 + 5 + 6 + 8)^5 \\
 & := (226 + 63 + 4 + 95 + 9 - 3 - 6)^4 & & := (-2 + 2 + 87 + 7 + 5 - 7 + 7 + 5 + 6 + 8)^5 \\
 & := (226 + 63 + 4 + 95 - 9 + 3 + 6)^4 & & := (-2 - 2 + 87 + 7 - 5 + 7 + 7 + 5 + 6 + 8)^5 \\
 & := (226 + 63 - 4 + 9 - 5 + 93 + 6)^4 & & := (2 - 2 + 87 - 7 + 5 + 7 + 7 + 5 + 6 + 8)^5 \\
 & := (226 + 63 + 4 - 9 + 5 + 93 + 6)^4 & & := (-2 + 2 + 87 - 7 + 5 + 7 + 7 + 5 + 6 + 8)^5 \\
 & := (226 + 6 + 3 + 49 + 5 + 93 + 6)^4 & & := (2 + 2 + 8 + 7 + 7 + 5 + 7 + 7 + 5 + 68)^5 \\
 & := (-22 + 66 + 349 - 5 + 9 - 3 - 6)^4 & & := (22 + 87 + 7 - 5 + 7 + 7 - 5 + 6 - 8)^5 \\
 & := (-22 + 66 + 349 - 5 - 9 + 3 + 6)^4 & & := (22 + 87 + 7 + 5 + 7 - 7 - 5 - 6 + 8)^5 \\
 & := (2 + 266 + 3 + 49 + 59 + 3 + 6)^4 & & := (22 + 87 + 7 + 5 - 7 + 7 - 5 - 6 + 8)^5 \\
 & := (2 + 2 + 6 + 6 + 349 + 59 - 36)^4 & & := (22 + 87 - 7 + 5 + 7 + 7 - 5 - 6 + 8)^5 \\
 & := (226 + 63 + 49 + 59 - 3 - 6)^4 & & := (22 + 87 + 7 - 5 + 7 - 7 + 5 - 6 + 8)^5 \\
 & := (226 + 63 + 49 + 5 + 9 + 36)^4 & & := (22 + 87 + 7 - 5 + 7 - 7 + 5 - 6 + 8)^5 \\
 & := (226 + 6 + 34 + 95 - 9 + 36)^4 & & := (22 + 87 + 7 - 5 - 7 + 7 + 5 - 6 + 8)^5 \\
 & := (2 + 266 + 34 - 9 + 59 + 36)^4 & & := (22 + 87 - 7 - 5 + 7 + 7 + 5 - 6 + 8)^5
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 &:= (-2+28+7+7+5+7-7+5+68)^5 & &:= (-22+8-7+75+7-7+56+8)^5 \\
 &:= (-2+28+7+7+5-7+7+5+68)^5 & &:= (-22+8-7+75-7+7+56+8)^5 \\
 &:= (-2+28+7-7+5+7+7+5+68)^5 & &:= (22-8-7-7+57+75-6-8)^5 \\
 &:= (-2+28-7+7+5+7+7+5+68)^5 & &:= (-22+8+7+7+57+75-6-8)^5 \\
 &:= (2+2-8+77+57+7-5-6-8)^5 & &:= (-22-8+7+7+57+75-6+8)^5 \\
 &:= (-2-2-8+77+57-7+5+6-8)^5 & &:= (-22+8-7-7+57+75+6+8)^5 \\
 &:= (-2-2-8+77-5+77-5-6-8)^5 & &:= (-22+8-7-7+5+77+56+8)^5 \\
 &:= (2-2-8+77-5-7+75-6-8)^5 & &:= (2-28+77+57+7+5+6-8)^5 \\
 &:= (-2+2-8+77-5-7+75-6-8)^5 & &:= (-2-28+77+57+7+5-6+8)^5 \\
 &:= (2+2+8+77-5-7-7+56-8)^5 & &:= (-2-28+77+5-7+75+6-8)^5 \\
 &:= (-2-2-8+77+5+7-7+56-8)^5 & &:= (2-28+77+5+7+7+56-8)^5 \\
 &:= (-2-2-8+77+5-7+7+56-8)^5 & &:= (-2-28-7+75+77+5+6-8)^5 \\
 &:= (2+2-8+77-5-7-7+56+8)^5 & &:= (-2-28+7+75-7+75+6-8)^5 \\
 &:= (2-2-8-7+75+77-5-6-8)^5 & &:= (-2-28-7+75+7+75+6-8)^5 \\
 &:= (-2+2-8-7+75+77-5-6-8)^5 & &:= (2-28+7+75+7+7+56-8)^5 \\
 &:= (2+2-8-7+75-7+75-6-8)^5 & &:= (2-28+7+7+57+75+6-8)^5 \\
 &:= (-2-2-8+7+75+7-7+56-8)^5 & &:= (-2-28+7+7+57+75-6+8)^5 \\
 &:= (-2-2-8+7+75-7+7+56-8)^5 & &:= (2-28+7+7+5+77+56-8)^5 \\
 &:= (-2-2-8-7+75+7+7+56-8)^5 & &:= (2+2+87+75+7-7-56+8)^5 \\
 &:= (-2-2-8+7-7+57+75+6-8)^5 & &:= (2+2+87+75-7+7-56+8)^5 \\
 &:= (-2-2-8-7+7+57+75+6-8)^5 & &:= (2+2+87+7-57+75-6+8)^5 \\
 &:= (2-2-8+7+7+57+7+56-8)^5 & &:= (2-2+87+7-5+77-56+8)^5 \\
 &:= (-2+2-8+7+7+57+7+56-8)^5 & &:= (-2+2+87+7-5+77-56+8)^5 \\
 &:= (-2-2+8+7-7+57-7+56+8)^5 & &:= (2+2+87-7+5+77-56+8)^5 \\
 &:= (-2-2+8-7+7+57-7+56+8)^5 & &:= (22+87-75+77+5-6+8)^5 \\
 &:= (-2-2+8-7-7+57+7+56+8)^5 & &:= (22+87+75+7-75-6+8)^5 \\
 &:= (2+2+8-7-7-5+77+56-8)^5 & &:= (22+87-75+7+75-6+8)^5 \\
 &:= (-2-2-8+7-7+5+77+56-8)^5 & &:= (22+87-7-57+75+6-8)^5 \\
 &:= (-2-2-8-7+7+5+77+56-8)^5 & &:= (22+87+7+57-7-56+8)^5 \\
 &:= (2+2-8-7-7-5+77+56+8)^5 & &:= (22+87-7+57+7-56+8)^5 \\
 &:= (-22+8+77+57+7+5-6-8)^5 & &:= (2+287-75-77-5-6-8)^5 \\
 &:= (-22-8+77+57+7+5-6+8)^5 & &:= (2+287-75-7-75-6-8)^5 \\
 &:= (-22-8+77+5-7+75+6-8)^5 & &:= (-2-2-8+775-77-568)^5 \\
 &:= (-22+8+77+5-7-7+56+8)^5 & &:= (22+87+757-756+8)^5 \\
 &:= (-22-8-7+75+77+5+6-8)^5 & &:= **22882115719** := (2+2882+1+1-57+1+9)^3 \\
 &:= (-22-8+7+75-7+75+6-8)^5 & &:= (2-2882+1-1+5719)^3 \\
 &:= (-22-8-7+75+7+75+6-8)^5 & &:= (2-2882-1+1+5719)^3 \\
 &:= (-22+8+7+75-7-7+56+8)^5 & &:= **22898045041** := (-2-2-8-98-04+504-1)^4
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 & := (-22 + 8 - 98 - 04 + 504 + 1)^4 \\
 & := (2 - 2 + 898 - 04 - 504 - 1)^4 \\
 & := (-2 + 2 + 898 - 04 - 504 - 1)^4 \\
 & := (2 + 2 - 8 - 98 + 0450 + 41)^4 \\
 \mathbf{22930509321} & := (2 + 2930 + 5 - 093 - 2 - 1)^3 \\
 & := (-2 + 2930 + 5 - 093 + 2 - 1)^3 \\
 \mathbf{22954731688} & := (2 + 2954 - 7 - 31 - 68 - 8)^3 \\
 & := (2 + 2954 - 7 - 3 - 16 - 88)^3 \\
 & := (229 - 547 + 3168 - 8)^3 \\
 \mathbf{22978971107} & := (-2 + 2978 - 9 - 7 - 110 - 7)^3 \\
 \mathbf{23246731864} & := (2 + 3 + 2467 + 318 + 64)^3 \\
 \mathbf{23271176375} & := (2 - 3 + 2711 + 7 + 63 + 75)^3 \\
 \mathbf{23295638016} & := (2 - 3 + 2956 - 3 - 80 - 16)^3 \\
 \mathbf{23372600161} & := (2 + 3 + 372 + 6 + 001 + 6 + 1)^4 \\
 & := (2 + 337 - 2 + 60 + 01 - 6 - 1)^4 \\
 & := (-2 + 337 + 2 + 60 + 01 - 6 - 1)^4 \\
 & := (2 + 337 - 2 + 60 - 01 - 6 + 1)^4 \\
 & := (-2 + 337 + 2 + 60 - 01 - 6 + 1)^4 \\
 & := (2 + 337 - 2 - 6 - 001 + 61)^4 \\
 & := (-2 + 337 + 2 - 6 - 001 + 61)^4 \\
 & := (233 - 7 - 2 + 6 + 00161)^4 \\
 & := (-233 + 7 + 2 + 600 + 16 - 1)^4 \\
 \mathbf{23393656000} & := (2 + 3393 + 65 - 600 + 0)^3 \\
 \mathbf{23442767928} & := (-2 - 3 + 4 - 4 + 2767 + 92 + 8)^3 \\
 \mathbf{23442767928} & := (-2 - 3 - 4 + 4 + 2767 + 92 + 8)^3 \\
 \mathbf{23467349647} & := (2346 + 7 + 3 + 496 + 4 + 7)^3 \\
 \mathbf{23491948544} & := (2349 + 19 - 48 + 544)^3 \\
 \mathbf{23612624896} & := (2 + 361 + 2 + 6 + 2 - 4 + 8 + 9 + 6)^4 \\
 & := (2 + 361 - 2 + 6 - 2 + 4 + 8 + 9 + 6)^4 \\
 & := (-2 + 361 + 2 + 6 - 2 + 4 + 8 + 9 + 6)^4 \\
 & := (-2 + 361 - 2 + 6 + 2 + 4 + 8 + 9 + 6)^4 \\
 & := (2 + 361 + 26 + 2 - 4 + 8 - 9 + 6)^4 \\
 & := (-2 + 361 + 26 - 2 + 4 + 8 - 9 + 6)^4 \\
 & := (-2 + 361 - 2 + 62 - 4 - 8 - 9 - 6)^4 \\
 & := (-2 + 361 - 2 + 6 + 24 + 8 - 9 + 6)^4 \\
 & := (-236 + 1 - 2 + 624 + 8 - 9 + 6)^4 \\
 & := (-236 - 1 - 2 + 624 - 8 + 9 + 6)^4 \\
 & := (236 + 1 + 2 + 62 - 4 + 89 + 6)^4 \\
 & := (23 + 6 + 1 + 262 - 4 + 8 + 96)^4 \\
 & := (2 + 36 + 1 + 262 - 4 + 89 + 6)^4 \\
 & := (-2 - 36 - 1 - 2 - 62 + 489 + 6)^4 \\
 & := (-2 - 3 + 61 - 2 - 6 + 248 + 96)^4 \\
 & := (-23 + 61 + 262 + 4 - 8 + 96)^4 \\
 & := (-23 + 6 - 12 - 62 + 489 - 6)^4 \\
 & := (-23 - 6 - 12 - 62 + 489 + 6)^4 \\
 & := (-2 + 361 - 26 - 24 + 89 - 6)^4 \\
 \mathbf{23639903000} & := (2 - 36 + 3 - 99 + 03000)^3 \\
 & := (2 - 36 + 3 - 9 - 90 + 3000)^3 \\
 & := (2 + 3 - 6 - 39 - 90 + 3000)^3 \\
 \mathbf{23664622311} & := (-2 + 3 - 6 + 646 + 2231 - 1)^3 \\
 & := (2 - 3 - 6 + 646 + 2231 + 1)^3 \\
 \mathbf{23689358848} & := (-23 - 689 + 3588 + 4 - 8)^3 \\
 \mathbf{23854493601} & := (2 + 38 - 5 + 4 + 4 - 9 + 360 - 1)^4 \\
 & := (-2 + 38 + 5 + 4 - 4 - 9 + 360 + 1)^4 \\
 & := (-2 + 38 + 5 - 4 + 4 - 9 + 360 + 1)^4 \\
 & := (-2 + 38 - 5 - 4 - 4 + 9 + 360 + 1)^4 \\
 & := (-2 + 3 - 8 + 54 - 4 - 9 + 360 - 1)^4 \\
 & := (2 - 3 - 8 + 54 - 4 - 9 + 360 + 1)^4 \\
 & := (2 + 3 + 8 - 5 + 449 - 3 - 60 - 1)^4 \\
 & := (-2 - 3 + 8 + 5 + 449 - 3 - 60 - 1)^4 \\
 & := (2 - 3 + 8 - 5 + 449 + 3 - 60 - 1)^4 \\
 & := (2 + 3 - 8 + 5 + 449 + 3 - 60 - 1)^4 \\
 & := (238 - 5 + 4 + 4 + 93 + 60 - 1)^4 \\
 & := (-23 + 8 + 54 + 4 - 9 + 360 - 1)^4 \\
 & := (-2 + 385 - 4 + 49 - 36 + 01)^4 \\
 & := (-2 - 38 + 5 - 4 + 493 - 60 - 1)^4 \\
 & := (-2 - 38 - 5 + 4 + 493 - 60 + 1)^4 \\
 & := (-2 - 3 + 8 + 544 - 93 - 60 - 1)^4 \\
 & := (2 + 3 + 8 - 54 + 493 - 60 + 1)^4 \\
 & := (23 - 8 - 54 + 493 - 60 - 1)^4 \\
 & := (-2 + 385 + 44 - 93 + 60 - 1)^4 \\
 \mathbf{23862997439} & := (-2 + 3862 - 997 + 4 + 3 + 9)^3 \\
 \mathbf{23863536599} & := (2 + 3 + 86 + 3 + 5 + 3 - 6 + 5 + 9 + 9)^5 \\
 & := (2 + 3 + 86 - 3 + 5 - 3 + 6 + 5 + 9 + 9)^5 \\
 & := (2 - 3 + 86 + 3 + 5 - 3 + 6 + 5 + 9 + 9)^5 \\
 & := (2 - 3 + 86 - 3 + 5 + 3 + 6 + 5 + 9 + 9)^5
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} &:= (23 + 86 + 3 + 5 + 3 - 6 + 5 + 9 - 9)^5 &:= (-2 + 3 - 8 - 6 - 3 - 5 + 36 + 5 + 99)^5 \\ &:= (23 + 86 - 3 + 5 - 3 + 6 + 5 + 9 - 9)^5 &:= (-2 - 3 - 8 - 6 + 3 - 5 + 36 + 5 + 99)^5 \\ &:= (23 + 86 + 3 + 5 + 3 - 6 + 5 - 9 + 9)^5 &:= (23 + 8 - 6 + 35 + 36 + 5 + 9 + 9)^5 \\ &:= (23 + 86 - 3 + 5 - 3 + 6 + 5 - 9 + 9)^5 &:= (23 + 8 + 6 + 35 + 3 - 6 + 59 - 9)^5 \\ &:= (23 + 8 + 63 + 5 + 3 - 6 + 5 + 9 + 9)^5 &:= (23 + 8 - 6 + 35 + 3 + 6 + 59 - 9)^5 \\ &:= (23 + 8 + 6 - 3 + 5 - 3 + 65 + 9 + 9)^5 &:= (23 + 8 - 6 + 35 - 3 - 6 + 59 + 9)^5 \\ &:= (23 + 8 - 6 + 3 + 5 + 3 + 65 + 9 + 9)^5 &:= (23 + 8 - 6 - 3 + 53 - 6 + 59 - 9)^5 \\ &:= (2 + 38 + 6 + 3 + 53 - 6 + 5 + 9 + 9)^5 &:= (-23 - 8 + 6 + 3 + 53 - 6 - 5 + 99)^5 \\ &:= (2 + 38 - 6 + 3 + 53 + 6 + 5 + 9 + 9)^5 &:= (-23 - 8 - 6 + 3 + 53 + 6 - 5 + 99)^5 \\ &:= (2 + 38 + 6 + 3 + 5 + 3 - 6 + 59 + 9)^5 &:= (23 + 8 - 6 + 3 + 5 + 36 + 59 - 9)^5 \\ &:= (2 + 38 + 6 - 3 + 5 - 3 + 6 + 59 + 9)^5 &:= (-23 + 8 + 6 + 3 - 5 + 36 - 5 + 99)^5 \\ &:= (2 + 38 - 6 + 3 + 5 + 3 + 6 + 59 + 9)^5 &:= (-2 - 38 + 63 + 5 + 3 - 6 - 5 + 99)^5 \\ &:= (-2 + 38 + 6 - 3 - 5 - 3 - 6 - 5 + 99)^5 &:= (2 - 38 + 63 - 5 - 3 + 6 - 5 + 99)^5 \\ &:= (-2 + 38 - 6 + 3 - 5 + 3 - 6 - 5 + 99)^5 &:= (-2 - 38 + 63 - 5 + 3 - 6 + 5 + 99)^5 \\ &:= (-2 + 38 - 6 - 3 - 5 - 3 + 6 - 5 + 99)^5 &:= (2 + 38 - 6 + 35 + 3 + 65 - 9 - 9)^5 \\ &:= (2 - 3 + 8 + 63 + 5 - 3 + 65 - 9 - 9)^5 &:= (-2 - 38 + 6 - 3 - 5 - 3 + 65 + 99)^5 \\ &:= (-2 + 3 - 8 + 63 - 5 + 3 + 65 + 9 - 9)^5 &:= (-2 - 38 - 6 + 3 - 5 + 3 + 65 + 99)^5 \\ &:= (-2 + 3 - 8 + 63 - 5 + 3 + 65 - 9 + 9)^5 &:= (-2 + 3 + 86 - 3 - 53 - 6 - 5 + 99)^5 \\ &:= (2 + 3 + 8 + 6 + 35 + 3 - 6 + 59 + 9)^5 &:= (-2 - 3 + 86 + 3 - 53 - 6 - 5 + 99)^5 \\ &:= (2 - 3 + 8 + 6 + 35 - 3 + 6 + 59 + 9)^5 &:= (2 - 3 + 86 - 3 + 5 - 36 + 59 + 9)^5 \\ &:= (2 + 3 + 8 - 6 + 35 + 3 + 6 + 59 + 9)^5 &:= (-2 + 3 + 8 + 63 - 53 + 6 - 5 + 99)^5 \\ &:= (-2 + 3 - 8 + 6 + 35 - 3 - 6 - 5 + 99)^5 &:= (-2 - 3 + 8 + 63 - 5 - 36 - 5 + 99)^5 \\ &:= (-2 - 3 - 8 + 6 + 35 + 3 - 6 - 5 + 99)^5 &:= (-2 + 3 - 8 + 63 + 5 - 36 - 5 + 99)^5 \\ &:= (-2 + 3 - 8 - 6 + 35 - 3 + 6 - 5 + 99)^5 &:= (-2 + 3 - 8 + 63 - 5 - 36 + 5 + 99)^5 \\ &:= (-2 - 3 - 8 - 6 + 35 + 3 + 6 - 5 + 99)^5 &:= (-2 - 3 - 8 + 6 - 35 - 3 + 65 + 99)^5 \\ &:= (2 + 3 + 8 + 6 + 3 + 53 - 6 + 59 - 9)^5 &:= (-2 + 3 - 8 - 6 - 35 + 3 + 65 + 99)^5 \\ &:= (2 - 3 + 8 + 6 - 3 + 53 + 6 + 59 - 9)^5 &:= (-238 - 6 + 3 - 5 + 365 + 9 - 9)^5 \\ &:= (2 + 3 + 8 - 6 + 3 + 53 + 6 + 59 - 9)^5 &:= (-238 - 6 + 3 - 5 + 365 - 9 + 9)^5 \\ &:= (2 + 3 + 8 - 6 - 3 + 53 - 6 + 59 + 9)^5 &:= (-23 + 86 - 35 + 3 - 6 - 5 + 99)^5 \\ &:= (2 - 3 + 8 - 6 + 3 + 53 - 6 + 59 + 9)^5 &:= (-23 + 86 + 3 - 5 - 36 - 5 + 99)^5 \\ &:= (-2 - 3 - 8 - 6 - 3 + 53 - 6 - 5 + 99)^5 &:= (23 + 8 - 63 + 53 - 6 + 5 + 99)^5 \\ &:= (2 - 3 + 8 + 6 - 3 + 5 + 36 + 59 + 9)^5 &:= (-2 - 38 - 6 + 35 + 36 - 5 + 99)^5 \\ &:= (2 + 3 + 8 - 6 + 3 + 5 + 36 + 59 + 9)^5 &:= (-23 - 8 + 63 + 53 - 65 + 99)^5 \\ &:= (-2 - 3 + 8 - 6 - 3 - 5 + 36 - 5 + 99)^5 &:= (-2 + 386 - 353 - 6 - 5 + 99)^5 \\ &:= (2 - 3 - 8 + 6 - 3 - 5 + 36 - 5 + 99)^5 &:= (-2 + 3 - 8 + 63 - 536 + 599)^5 \\ &:= (2 + 3 - 8 - 6 + 3 - 5 + 36 - 5 + 99)^5 &:= (-23 + 863 - 53 - 659 - 9)^5 \\ &:= (-2 + 3 - 8 - 6 - 3 + 5 + 36 - 5 + 99)^5 &:= (-2 + 3 + 8 + 878 - 7 + 2000)^3 \\ &:= (-2 - 3 - 8 - 6 + 3 + 5 + 36 - 5 + 99)^5 &:= (2 + 3 + 88 + 787 + 2000)^3 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{23912763841} &:= (23 + 9 + 1 + 2763 + 84 + 1)^3 &:= (2 - 4 + 2882 - 19 - 1 + 36)^3 \\ \mathbf{23937672968} &:= (-2 + 3 - 93 + 7 + 6 - 7 + 2968)^3 &:= (-24 + 2882 + 19 + 13 + 6)^3 \\ &:= (2 - 3 - 93 + 7 - 6 + 7 + 2968)^3 & \\ &:= (-2 + 3 - 93 - 7 + 6 + 7 + 2968)^3 & \mathbf{24313388273} := (2431 + 3 + 388 + 2 + 73)^3 \\ &:= (-2 - 3 - 9 - 3 - 76 + 7 + 2968)^3 & \mathbf{24343800625} := (2 + 434 - 38 - 006 - 2 + 5)^4 \\ &:= (-23 + 9 - 3 - 76 + 7 + 2968)^3 &:= (-2 + 434 - 38 - 006 + 2 + 5)^4 \\ & &:= (-2 - 4 + 34 + 380 - 06 - 2 - 5)^4 \\ \mathbf{24098215696} &:= (2 + 409 + 8 + 2 - 1 - 5 - 6 - 9 - 6)^4 & \mathbf{24363778699} := (2436 + 377 + 86 + 9 - 9)^3 \\ &:= (-2 + 409 - 8 - 2 + 1 + 5 + 6 - 9 - 6)^4 &:= (2436 + 377 + 86 - 9 + 9)^3 \\ &:= (2 + 409 - 8 - 2 + 1 - 5 - 6 + 9 - 6)^4 &:= (2436 + 377 + 8 + 69 + 9)^3 \\ &:= (-2 + 409 - 8 + 2 + 1 - 5 - 6 + 9 - 6)^4 &:= (-24 + 3637 - 7 - 8 - 699)^3 \\ &:= (-2 + 409 - 8 - 2 + 1 + 5 - 6 - 9 + 6)^4 & \mathbf{24415625025} := (2 + 4 - 4 + 156250 - 2 + 5)^2 \\ &:= (-2 + 409 - 8 - 2 - 1 - 5 + 6 - 9 + 6)^4 &:= (2 - 4 + 4 + 156250 - 2 + 5)^2 \\ &:= (-2 + 409 - 8 + 21 - 5 - 6 - 9 - 6)^4 &:= (-2 + 4 - 4 + 156250 + 2 + 5)^2 \\ &:= (2 + 409 + 8 - 21 + 5 + 6 - 9 - 6)^4 &:= (-2 - 4 + 4 + 156250 + 2 + 5)^2 \\ &:= (2 + 409 + 8 - 21 + 5 - 6 - 9 + 6)^4 &:= (-24 + 4 + 156250 + 25)^2 \\ &:= (-2 + 409 - 8 - 21 - 5 + 6 + 9 + 6)^4 & \mathbf{24591257856} := (-2 + 459 + 1 - 2 - 57 + 8 - 5 - 6)^4 \\ &:= (240 + 98 - 2 - 1 + 56 + 9 - 6)^4 &:= (2 + 459 - 1 + 2 - 57 - 8 + 5 - 6)^4 \\ &:= (240 + 98 + 2 + 1 + 56 - 9 + 6)^4 &:= (2 + 459 + 1 - 2 - 57 - 8 - 5 + 6)^4 \\ &:= (240 - 9 + 82 + 1 + 5 + 69 + 6)^4 &:= (-2 + 459 + 1 + 2 - 57 - 8 - 5 + 6)^4 \\ &:= (240 - 9 + 8 + 2 + 156 - 9 + 6)^4 &:= (2 + 459 - 1 - 2 + 5 - 78 + 5 + 6)^4 \\ &:= (240 + 9 - 8 + 2 - 1 + 56 + 96)^4 &:= (-2 + 459 - 1 + 2 + 5 - 78 + 5 + 6)^4 \\ &:= (240 - 9 + 8 + 2 + 1 + 56 + 96)^4 &:= (2 + 459 - 1 + 2 + 5 - 7 - 8 - 56)^4 \\ &:= (-2 - 409 + 821 + 5 - 6 - 9 - 6)^4 &:= (2 + 459 - 1 - 2 - 5 + 7 - 8 - 56)^4 \\ &:= (-2 + 409 - 82 + 1 + 5 + 69 - 6)^4 &:= (-2 + 459 - 1 + 2 - 5 + 7 - 8 - 56)^4 \\ &:= (-2 + 409 - 82 - 1 - 5 + 69 + 6)^4 &:= (-2 + 459 + 1 - 2 - 5 - 7 + 8 - 56)^4 \\ &:= (2 + 4 + 098 + 215 + 69 + 6)^4 &:= (245 + 91 - 2 - 5 + 78 - 5 - 6)^4 \\ &:= (-24 + 0982 - 1 - 569 + 6)^4 &:= (245 + 91 - 2 + 5 - 7 + 8 + 56)^4 \\ &:= (2 + 40 + 98 + 2 + 156 + 96)^4 &:= (245 + 9 + 1 + 2 + 5 + 78 + 56)^4 \\ \mathbf{24112521369} &:= (2411 + 2 + 521 - 36 - 9)^3 &:= (24 + 5 + 91 + 257 + 8 + 5 + 6)^4 \\ &:= (2 + 411 + 2521 - 36 - 9)^3 &:= (2 + 459 + 12 - 5 + 7 - 85 + 6)^4 \\ \mathbf{24237932984} &:= (-2 + 42 - 37 - 93 + 2984)^3 &:= (2 + 459 - 1 + 25 - 78 - 5 - 6)^4 \\ \mathbf{24288219136} &:= (2 + 4 + 2882 + 1 + 9 + 1 + 3 - 6)^3 &:= (2 + 459 + 1 - 25 + 7 + 8 - 56)^4 \\ &:= (-2 + 4 + 2882 + 1 + 9 - 1 - 3 + 6)^3 &:= (2 - 459 + 1 - 2 + 5 - 7 + 856)^4 \\ &:= (-2 + 4 + 2882 - 1 + 9 + 1 - 3 + 6)^3 &:= (-2 - 459 + 1 + 2 + 5 - 7 + 856)^4 \\ &:= (2 - 4 + 2882 - 1 + 9 - 1 + 3 + 6)^3 &:= (-2 - 459 + 1 - 2 - 5 + 7 + 856)^4 \\ &:= (-2 - 4 + 2882 + 1 + 9 + 1 + 3 + 6)^3 &:= (-2 + 4 + 59 - 1 + 257 + 85 - 6)^4 \\ &:= (24 + 2882 + 1 - 9 + 1 + 3 - 6)^3 &:= (245 - 9 + 12 + 57 + 85 + 6)^4 \\ &:= (-2 + 4 + 2882 + 19 - 13 + 6)^3 &:= (245 - 9 + 1 + 25 + 78 + 56)^4 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} & := (2 - 45 + 91 + 257 + 85 + 6)^4 \\ & := (2 - 4 + 591 - 257 + 8 + 56)^4 \\ \mathbf{24718462497} & := (2471 - 8 + 462 + 4 - 9 - 7)^3 \\ \mathbf{24769410875} & := (2476 + 9 + 410 + 8 + 7 + 5)^3 \\ \mathbf{24794911296} & := (2 + 4 + 7 + 9 + 4 + 9 + 1 + 1 + 2 + 9 + 6)^6 \\ & := (24 + 7 + 9 + 4 + 9 + 1 - 1 - 2 + 9 - 6)^6 \\ & := (24 + 7 + 9 + 4 + 9 - 1 + 1 - 2 + 9 - 6)^6 \\ & := (24 + 7 + 9 + 4 + 9 + 1 + 1 + 2 - 9 + 6)^6 \\ & := (24 - 7 + 9 + 4 + 9 + 1 + 1 - 2 + 9 + 6)^6 \\ & := (24 - 7 + 9 + 4 + 9 - 1 - 1 + 2 + 9 + 6)^6 \\ & := (24 + 7 + 9 + 4 - 9 + 1 + 1 + 2 + 9 + 6)^6 \\ & := (24 + 7 - 9 + 4 + 9 + 1 + 1 + 2 + 9 + 6)^6 \\ & := (2 + 47 + 9 + 4 + 9 + 1 - 1 - 2 - 9 - 6)^6 \\ & := (2 + 47 + 9 + 4 + 9 - 1 + 1 - 2 - 9 - 6)^6 \\ & := (-2 + 47 + 9 + 4 + 9 + 1 - 1 + 2 - 9 - 6)^6 \\ & := (-2 + 47 + 9 + 4 + 9 - 1 + 1 + 2 - 9 - 6)^6 \\ & := (2 + 47 + 9 + 4 - 9 + 1 - 1 - 2 + 9 - 6)^6 \\ & := (2 + 47 - 9 + 4 + 9 + 1 - 1 - 2 + 9 - 6)^6 \\ & := (2 + 47 + 9 + 4 - 9 - 1 + 1 - 2 + 9 - 6)^6 \\ & := (2 + 47 - 9 + 4 + 9 - 1 + 1 - 2 + 9 - 6)^6 \\ & := (-2 + 47 + 9 + 4 - 9 + 1 - 1 + 2 + 9 - 6)^6 \\ & := (-2 + 47 - 9 + 4 + 9 + 1 - 1 + 2 + 9 - 6)^6 \\ & := (-2 + 47 + 9 + 4 - 9 - 1 + 1 + 2 + 9 - 6)^6 \\ & := (-2 + 47 - 9 + 4 + 9 - 1 + 1 + 2 + 9 - 6)^6 \\ & := (-2 + 47 + 9 - 4 + 9 + 1 - 1 - 2 - 9 + 6)^6 \\ & := (-2 + 47 + 9 - 4 + 9 - 1 + 1 - 2 - 9 + 6)^6 \\ & := (2 + 47 + 9 + 4 - 9 + 1 + 1 + 2 - 9 + 6)^6 \\ & := (2 + 47 - 9 + 4 + 9 + 1 + 1 + 2 - 9 + 6)^6 \\ & := (-2 + 47 + 9 - 4 - 9 + 1 - 1 - 2 + 9 + 6)^6 \\ & := (-2 + 47 - 9 - 4 + 9 + 1 - 1 - 2 + 9 + 6)^6 \\ & := (-2 + 47 + 9 - 4 - 9 - 1 + 1 - 2 + 9 + 6)^6 \\ & := (-2 + 47 - 9 - 4 + 9 - 1 + 1 - 2 + 9 + 6)^6 \\ & := (2 + 47 - 9 + 4 - 9 + 1 + 1 + 2 + 9 + 6)^6 \\ & := (2 + 4 + 7 + 9 + 49 + 1 - 1 - 2 - 9 - 6)^6 \\ & := (2 + 4 + 7 + 9 + 49 - 1 + 1 - 2 - 9 - 6)^6 \\ & := (-2 + 4 + 7 + 9 + 49 + 1 - 1 + 2 - 9 - 6)^6 \\ & := (-2 + 4 + 7 + 9 + 49 - 1 + 1 + 2 - 9 - 6)^6 \\ & := (2 + 4 - 7 + 9 + 49 + 1 - 1 + 2 + 9 - 6)^6 \\ & := (2 + 4 + 7 - 9 + 49 - 1 + 1 + 2 + 9 - 6)^6 \\ & := (-2 + 4 - 7 + 9 + 49 + 1 + 1 + 2 - 9 + 6)^6 \\ & := (-2 - 4 + 7 + 9 + 49 + 1 - 1 - 2 - 9 + 6)^6 \\ & := (-2 - 4 + 7 + 9 + 49 - 1 + 1 - 2 - 9 + 6)^6 \\ & := (2 + 4 - 7 + 9 + 49 + 1 + 1 - 2 - 9 + 6)^6 \\ & := (2 + 4 + 7 - 9 + 49 - 1 - 1 + 2 - 9 + 6)^6 \\ & := (-2 + 4 - 7 + 9 + 49 + 1 + 1 + 2 - 9 + 6)^6 \\ & := (-2 + 4 + 7 + 9 + 4 + 9 + 1 - 1 + 29 - 6)^6 \\ & := (-2 + 4 + 7 + 9 + 4 + 9 - 1 + 1 + 29 - 6)^6 \\ & := (2 + 4 - 7 + 9 + 4 + 9 - 1 - 1 + 29 + 6)^6 \\ & := (2 - 4 + 7 + 9 - 4 + 9 + 1 - 1 + 29 + 6)^6 \\ & := (2 - 4 + 7 + 9 - 4 + 9 - 1 + 1 + 29 + 6)^6 \\ & := (2 + 4 + 7 + 9 + 4 - 9 + 1 + 1 + 29 + 6)^6 \\ & := (2 + 4 + 7 - 9 + 4 + 9 + 1 + 1 + 29 + 6)^6 \\ & := (-2 + 4 - 7 + 9 + 4 + 9 + 1 + 1 + 29 + 6)^6 \\ & := (24 + 7 - 9 + 49 + 1 - 1 - 2 - 9 - 6)^6 \\ & := (24 + 7 - 9 + 49 - 1 + 1 - 2 - 9 - 6)^6 \\ & := (24 - 7 - 9 + 49 + 1 + 1 - 2 - 9 + 6)^6 \\ & := (24 - 7 - 9 + 49 - 1 - 1 + 2 - 9 + 6)^6 \\ & := (-24 + 7 + 9 + 49 + 1 - 1 - 2 + 9 + 6)^6 \\ & := (-24 + 7 + 9 + 49 - 1 + 1 - 2 + 9 + 6)^6 \\ & := (24 - 7 + 9 - 4 + 9 + 1 - 1 + 29 - 6)^6 \\ & := (24 - 7 + 9 - 4 + 9 - 1 + 1 + 29 - 6)^6 \\ & := (24 - 7 + 9 + 4 - 9 - 1 - 1 + 29 + 6)^6 \\ & := (24 - 7 - 9 + 4 + 9 - 1 - 1 + 29 + 6)^6 \\ & := (24 + 7 - 9 + 4 - 9 + 1 + 1 + 29 + 6)^6 \\ & := (-2 + 47 - 9 + 4 - 9 + 1 - 1 + 29 - 6)^6 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} & := (-2+47-9+4-9-1+1+29-6)^6 & := (2+47+94+9-1+1-2-96)^6 \\ & := (2-4+79-4+9-11-2-9-6)^6 & := (-2+47+94+9+1-1+2-96)^6 \\ & := (-2-4+79-4-9+11-2-9-6)^6 & := (-2+47+94+9-1+1+2-96)^6 \\ & := (-2-4+79-4+9-11+2-9-6)^6 & := (-2+47-94+9+1-1-2+96)^6 \\ & := (2-4+79-4-9-11-2+9-6)^6 & := (-2+47-94+9-1+1-2+96)^6 \\ & := (-2-4+79-4-9-11+2+9-6)^6 & := (2+47-9+49+1-1-29-6)^6 \\ & := (2-4+79-4+9-1-12-9-6)^6 & := (2+47-9+49-1+1-29-6)^6 \\ & := (2+4+79+4-9+1-12-9-6)^6 & := (2-47+9-4+91-12+9+6)^6 \\ & := (2-4+79-4-9-1-12+9-6)^6 & := (2+47+9+4+91-1-2-96)^6 \\ & := (-2+4+79-4-9+1-12-9+6)^6 & := (-2+47+9+4+91-1+2-96)^6 \\ & := (-2-4+79+4-9+1-12-9+6)^6 & := (-2+47+9-4-91+1-2+96)^6 \\ & := (-2+4-7+94-9+1-12-9-6)^6 & := (2-47+9-4+9+1-12+96)^6 \\ & := (2-4-7-9+49+1-1+29-6)^6 & := (-2-47+9-4-9-1+12+96)^6 \\ & := (2-4-7-9+49-1+1+29-6)^6 & := (-2-47-9-4+9-1+12+96)^6 \\ & := (-2+4-7-9+4+91-12-9-6)^6 & := (2-4+79-49-1+12+9+6)^6 \\ & := (2-4-7-9-4+91-12-9+6)^6 & := (-2+4-79+4+91+1+29+6)^6 \\ & := (2-4-7-9-4-9+1-12+96)^6 & := (-2-4+79-4+9+11-29-6)^6 \\ & := (24-79+4+91+1-2+9+6)^6 & := (2+4-79-4+9-1+129-6)^6 \\ & := (-24+79-4+9+11-2-9-6)^6 & := (2-4-79+4+9-1+129-6)^6 \\ & := (-24+79-4-9+11-2+9-6)^6 & := (-2-4-79-4+9-1+129+6)^6 \\ & := (-24+79-4+9-11+2+9-6)^6 & := (-2+4-79+4-9+1+129+6)^6 \\ & := (-24+79+4+9+1-12-9+6)^6 & := (2-4+7-94+9-1+129+6)^6 \\ & := (-24+79+4-9+1-12+9+6)^6 & := (-2+4+7+9-49+1-12+96)^6 \\ & := (24-79+4+9+1+1-2+96)^6 & := (2-4+7-9-49-1+12+96)^6 \\ & := (24-79+4+9-1-1+2+96)^6 & := (-2-4-7+9-49-1+12+96)^6 \\ & := (-24+7+94-9+1-12-9+6)^6 & := (-2+4+7+9+4-91+129-6)^6 \\ & := (24+7+9+49+1-1-29-6)^6 & := (2-4+7+9-4-91+129+6)^6 \\ & := (24+7+9+49-1+1-29-6)^6 & := (247-9+4-91+1-2-96)^6 \\ & := (24-7+9+49+1+1-29+6)^6 & := (24+79+49+1-1-2-96)^6 \\ & := (-24+7-9+4+91-12-9+6)^6 & := (24+79+49-1+1-2-96)^6 \\ & := (-24+7-9+4-9+1-12+96)^6 & := (24-79-4+91-1+29-6)^6 \\ & := (-24-7-9-4-9-1+12+96)^6 & := (-24+79-4-9-11+29-6)^6 \\ & := (2+47+94-91+1-2+9-6)^6 & := (24-79-4-9-1+129-6)^6 \\ & := (-2+47+94-91+1+2+9-6)^6 & := (24-7+94-91-1+29+6)^6 \\ & := (-2+47-94+91-1-2+9+6)^6 & := (24-7-94+9-1+129-6)^6 \\ & := (2-47+94+9-1+12-9-6)^6 & := (24-7+9-4-91+129-6)^6 \\ & := (2-47+94-9-1+12+9-6)^6 & := (247+94+9+1-1-296)^6 \\ & := (2+47+94+9+1-1-2-96)^6 & := (247+94+9-1+1-296)^6 \end{aligned}$$

$$:= (247 + 9 + 4 + 91 - 1 - 296)^6$$

$$\mathbf{24820429213} := (2482 + 0429 + 2 + 1 + 3)^3$$

$$\mathbf{24840596881} := (2 - 4 + 8 + 405 + 9 - 6 - 8 - 8 - 1)^4$$

$$:= (-2 + 4 - 8 + 405 + 9 + 6 - 8 - 8 - 1)^4$$

$$:= (2 - 4 - 8 + 405 + 9 - 6 + 8 - 8 - 1)^4$$

$$:= (2 - 4 - 8 + 405 + 9 - 6 - 8 + 8 - 1)^4$$

$$:= (-2 + 4 + 8 + 405 - 9 + 6 - 8 - 8 + 1)^4$$

$$:= (2 - 4 + 8 + 405 - 9 - 6 + 8 - 8 + 1)^4$$

$$:= (-2 + 4 - 8 + 405 - 9 + 6 + 8 - 8 + 1)^4$$

$$:= (2 - 4 + 8 + 405 - 9 - 6 - 8 + 8 + 1)^4$$

$$:= (-2 + 4 - 8 + 405 - 9 + 6 - 8 + 8 + 1)^4$$

$$:= (2 - 4 - 8 + 405 - 9 - 6 + 8 + 8 + 1)^4$$

$$:= (2 + 484 - 05 - 9 - 68 - 8 + 1)^4$$

$$:= (2 + 484 - 05 + 9 - 6 - 88 + 1)^4$$

$$:= (-2 + 484 + 05 - 9 + 6 - 88 + 1)^4$$

$$:= (248 + 40 + 5 + 9 + 6 + 88 + 1)^4$$

$$:= (248 + 40 + 5 + 9 + 6 + 8 + 81)^4$$

$$:= (248 + 4 + 05 - 9 + 68 + 81)^4$$

$$:= (248 - 4 - 05 + 9 + 68 + 81)^4$$

$$:= (2 - 484 - 05 + 9 - 6 + 881)^4$$

$$:= (-2 - 484 + 05 - 9 + 6 + 881)^4$$

$$:= (2 + 48 + 405 + 9 + 6 + 8 - 81)^4$$

$$:= (2 + 4 + 8 + 405 - 9 + 68 - 81)^4$$

$$:= (-248 - 40 + 5 - 9 + 688 + 1)^4$$

$$:= (-248 - 40 + 596 + 88 + 1)^4$$

$$:= (-248 - 40 + 596 + 8 + 81)^4$$

$$\mathbf{24948281448} := (-2 + 4 + 94 + 8 + 2814 - 4 + 8)^3$$

$$:= (-2 - 4 + 94 + 8 + 2814 + 4 + 8)^3$$

$$\mathbf{25025203125} := (-250 - 2 + 52 + 03125)^3$$

$$:= (2 + 50 - 252 + 03125)^3$$

$$\mathbf{25091827216} := (250 + 91 - 8 - 2 + 72 + 1 - 6)^4$$

$$:= (-2 + 50 + 91 - 8 + 272 + 1 - 6)^4$$

$$:= (250 + 91 + 82 - 7 - 2 - 16)^4$$

$$:= (250 - 9 + 182 - 7 - 2 - 16)^4$$

$$:= (250 + 9 + 1 + 82 + 72 - 16)^4$$

$$:= (-2 - 509 + 182 + 721 + 6)^4$$

$$\mathbf{25128011089} := (-2 + 51 + 2801 - 10 + 89)^3$$

$$\mathbf{25141590721} := (2 - 514 + 159072 + 1)^2$$

$$\mathbf{25282750375} := (25 + 2827 + 5 + 03 + 75)^3$$

$$:= (2528 + 27 + 5 + 0375)^3$$

$$\mathbf{25334470953} := (2533 - 4 + 470 - 9 - 53)^3$$

$$\mathbf{25344958401} := (2 + 5 + 3 - 4 - 4 + 9 - 5 - 8 + 401)^4$$

$$:= (2 - 5 - 3 + 4 + 4 + 9 - 5 - 8 + 401)^4$$

$$:= (2 + 5 + 3 + 4 - 4 - 9 + 5 - 8 + 401)^4$$

$$:= (2 + 5 + 3 - 4 + 4 - 9 + 5 - 8 + 401)^4$$

$$:= (-2 + 5 - 3 - 4 - 4 + 9 + 5 - 8 + 401)^4$$

$$:= (2 - 5 + 3 - 4 - 4 + 9 + 5 - 8 + 401)^4$$

$$:= (2 + 5 - 3 + 4 - 4 - 9 - 5 + 8 + 401)^4$$

$$:= (2 + 5 - 3 - 4 + 4 - 9 - 5 + 8 + 401)^4$$

$$:= (-2 - 5 + 3 + 4 + 4 - 9 - 5 + 8 + 401)^4$$

$$:= (2 - 5 - 3 - 4 - 4 + 9 - 5 + 8 + 401)^4$$

$$:= (2 - 5 - 3 + 4 - 4 - 9 + 5 + 8 + 401)^4$$

$$:= (2 - 5 - 3 - 4 + 4 - 9 + 5 + 8 + 401)^4$$

$$:= (25 + 3 - 4 - 4 - 9 - 5 - 8 + 401)^4$$

$$:= (-25 + 3 + 4 + 4 + 9 - 5 + 8 + 401)^4$$

$$:= (-2 - 5 + 344 + 9 + 58 - 4 - 01)^4$$

$$:= (-2 + 5 + 344 - 9 + 58 + 4 - 01)^4$$

$$:= (2 + 5 - 3 + 449 - 5 - 8 - 40 - 1)^4$$

$$:= (2 - 5 - 3 + 449 + 5 - 8 - 40 - 1)^4$$

$$:= (25 + 3 + 449 + 5 - 84 + 01)^4$$

$$:= (-25 + 3 + 449 + 5 + 8 - 40 - 1)^4$$

$$:= (2 + 534 - 49 - 5 - 84 + 01)^4$$

$$:= (2 - 53 + 4 + 495 - 8 - 40 - 1)^4$$

$$:= (2 + 53 - 4 - 4 + 9 - 58 + 401)^4$$

$$:= (2 - 53 + 4 - 4 - 9 + 58 + 401)^4$$

$$:= (2 - 53 - 4 + 4 - 9 + 58 + 401)^4$$

$$:= (-2 - 5 + 344 + 95 + 8 - 40 - 1)^4$$

$$:= (2 + 5 + 344 + 95 - 8 - 40 + 1)^4$$

$$:= (2 + 5 - 3 - 449 + 5 + 840 - 1)^4$$

$$:= (-2 + 53 + 4 - 495 + 840 - 1)^4$$

$$:= (2 - 5 - 344 - 95 + 840 + 1)^4$$

$$\mathbf{25398159424} := (-2 - 53 - 9 + 8 + 159424)^2$$

$$:= (-25 - 39 + 8 + 159424)^2$$

$$\mathbf{25457159809} := (-254 + 5 - 7 + 159809)^2$$

$$\mathbf{25516048384} := (2551 - 6 + 0483 - 84)^3$$

$$\mathbf{25803133875} := (2580 - 3 - 1 - 3 + 387 - 5)^3$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 \mathbf{25829338816} &:= (-2 - 58 + 2933 + 88 + 1 - 6)^3 &:= (2 + 5 + 9 - 3 - 7 + 4 - 2 - 4 + 6 + 01)^{10} \\
 &:= (-2 - 58 + 2933 + 8 + 81 - 6)^3 &:= (-2 - 5 + 9 - 3 + 7 + 4 - 2 - 4 + 6 + 01)^{10} \\
 &:= (2 - 58 + 2933 - 8 + 81 + 6)^3 &:= (2 - 5 + 9 - 3 + 7 - 4 + 2 - 4 + 6 + 01)^{10} \\
 &:= (2 - 5829 - 33 + 8816)^3 &:= (-2 + 5 + 9 - 3 - 7 + 4 + 2 - 4 + 6 + 01)^{10} \\
 \mathbf{25856961601} &:= (258 - 5 - 6 + 96 - 1 + 60 - 1)^4 &:= (2 - 5 + 9 + 3 - 7 + 4 + 2 - 4 + 6 + 01)^{10} \\
 &:= (258 + 5 - 6 - 9 - 6 + 160 - 1)^4 &:= (2 + 5 - 9 - 3 + 7 + 4 + 2 - 4 + 6 + 01)^{10} \\
 &:= (-2 + 585 - 6 - 9 - 6 - 160 - 1)^4 &:= (2 + 5 + 9 - 3 - 7 - 4 - 2 + 4 + 6 + 01)^{10} \\
 &:= (2 + 5 - 8 + 569 - 6 - 160 - 1)^4 &:= (-2 - 5 + 9 - 3 + 7 - 4 - 2 + 4 + 6 + 01)^{10} \\
 &:= (-2 - 5 - 8 + 569 + 6 - 160 + 1)^4 &:= (-2 - 5 + 9 + 3 - 7 + 4 - 2 + 4 + 6 + 01)^{10} \\
 &:= (-258 + 56 + 9 - 6 - 1 + 601)^4 &:= (-2 + 5 - 9 - 3 + 7 + 4 - 2 + 4 + 6 + 01)^{10} \\
 &:= (-2 - 5 - 8 + 56 + 961 - 601)^4 &:= (2 - 5 - 9 + 3 + 7 + 4 - 2 + 4 + 6 + 01)^{10} \\
 \mathbf{25934336000} &:= (2593 + 4 + 3 + 360 + 00)^3 &:= (-2 + 5 + 9 - 3 - 7 - 4 + 2 + 4 + 6 + 01)^{10} \\
 \mathbf{25937424601} &:= (2 + 5 + 9 - 3 + 7 + 4 - 2 - 4 - 6 - 01)^{10} &:= (2 - 5 + 9 + 3 - 7 - 4 + 2 + 4 + 6 + 01)^{10} \\
 &:= (-2 + 5 + 9 - 3 + 7 + 4 + 2 - 4 - 6 - 01)^{10} &:= (2 + 5 - 9 - 3 + 7 - 4 + 2 + 4 + 6 + 01)^{10} \\
 &:= (2 - 5 + 9 + 3 + 7 + 4 + 2 - 4 - 6 - 01)^{10} &:= (2 + 5 - 9 + 3 - 7 + 4 + 2 + 4 + 6 + 01)^{10} \\
 &:= (2 + 5 + 9 - 3 + 7 - 4 - 2 + 4 - 6 - 01)^{10} &:= (-2 - 5 - 9 + 3 + 7 + 4 + 2 + 4 + 6 + 01)^{10} \\
 &:= (2 + 5 + 9 + 3 - 7 + 4 - 2 + 4 - 6 - 01)^{10} &:= (25 - 9 - 3 + 7 + 4 - 2 - 4 - 6 - 01)^{10} \\
 &:= (-2 - 5 + 9 + 3 + 7 + 4 - 2 + 4 - 6 - 01)^{10} &:= (25 + 9 - 3 - 7 - 4 + 2 - 4 - 6 - 01)^{10} \\
 &:= (-2 + 5 + 9 - 3 + 7 - 4 + 2 + 4 - 6 - 01)^{10} &:= (25 - 9 - 3 + 7 - 4 - 2 + 4 - 6 - 01)^{10} \\
 &:= (2 - 5 + 9 + 3 + 7 - 4 + 2 + 4 - 6 - 01)^{10} &:= (25 - 9 + 3 - 7 + 4 - 2 + 4 - 6 - 01)^{10} \\
 &:= (-2 + 5 + 9 + 3 - 7 + 4 + 2 + 4 - 6 - 01)^{10} &:= (25 - 9 + 3 - 7 - 4 + 2 - 4 + 6 - 01)^{10} \\
 &:= (2 + 5 - 9 + 3 + 7 + 4 + 2 + 4 - 6 - 01)^{10} &:= (25 - 9 + 3 + 7 - 4 - 2 - 4 - 6 + 01)^{10} \\
 &:= (-2 + 5 + 9 - 3 + 7 - 4 - 2 - 4 + 6 - 01)^{10} &:= (25 - 9 - 3 - 7 + 4 + 2 + 4 - 6 + 01)^{10} \\
 &:= (2 - 5 + 9 + 3 + 7 - 4 - 2 - 4 + 6 - 01)^{10} &:= (25 - 9 - 3 - 7 + 4 - 2 - 4 + 6 + 01)^{10} \\
 &:= (-2 + 5 + 9 + 3 - 7 + 4 - 2 - 4 + 6 - 01)^{10} &:= (25 - 9 - 3 - 7 - 4 - 2 + 4 + 6 + 01)^{10} \\
 &:= (2 + 5 - 9 + 3 + 7 + 4 - 2 - 4 + 6 - 01)^{10} &:= (-25 + 9 + 3 + 7 + 4 + 2 + 4 + 6 + 01)^{10} \\
 &:= (2 + 5 + 9 + 3 - 7 - 4 + 2 - 4 + 6 - 01)^{10} &:= (-2 - 5 - 9 + 3 - 7 + 42 - 4 - 6 - 01)^{10} \\
 &:= (-2 - 5 + 9 + 3 + 7 - 4 + 2 - 4 + 6 - 01)^{10} &:= (2 - 5 - 9 - 3 - 7 + 42 - 4 - 6 + 01)^{10} \\
 &:= (-2 + 5 - 9 + 3 + 7 + 4 + 2 - 4 + 6 - 01)^{10} &:= (-2 - 5 + 9 + 3 - 7 - 4 + 24 - 6 - 01)^{10} \\
 &:= (-2 + 5 + 9 + 3 - 7 - 4 - 2 + 4 + 6 - 01)^{10} &:= (-2 + 5 - 9 - 3 + 7 - 4 + 24 - 6 - 01)^{10} \\
 &:= (2 + 5 - 9 + 3 + 7 - 4 - 2 + 4 + 6 - 01)^{10} &:= (2 - 5 - 9 + 3 + 7 - 4 + 24 - 6 - 01)^{10} \\
 &:= (-2 + 5 - 9 + 3 + 7 - 4 + 2 + 4 + 6 - 01)^{10} &:= (-2 + 5 - 9 + 3 - 7 + 4 + 24 - 6 - 01)^{10} \\
 &:= (2 - 5 + 9 - 3 - 7 + 4 + 2 + 4 + 6 - 01)^{10} &:= (2 + 5 + 9 + 3 + 7 + 4 - 24 + 6 - 01)^{10} \\
 &:= (2 + 5 + 9 + 3 + 7 - 4 - 2 - 4 - 6 + 01)^{10} &:= (2 - 5 - 9 - 3 - 7 + 4 + 24 + 6 - 01)^{10} \\
 &:= (-2 + 5 + 9 + 3 + 7 - 4 + 2 - 4 - 6 + 01)^{10} &:= (2 - 5 + 9 - 3 - 7 - 4 + 24 - 6 + 01)^{10} \\
 &:= (2 - 5 + 9 - 3 + 7 + 4 - 2 + 4 - 6 + 01)^{10} &:= (2 + 5 - 9 - 3 - 7 + 4 + 24 - 6 + 01)^{10} \\
 &:= (2 + 5 + 9 - 3 - 7 + 4 + 2 + 4 - 6 + 01)^{10} &:= (-2 - 5 - 9 - 3 + 7 + 4 + 24 - 6 + 01)^{10} \\
 &:= (-2 - 5 + 9 - 3 + 7 + 4 + 2 + 4 - 6 + 01)^{10} &:= (-2 + 5 - 9 - 3 - 7 - 4 + 24 + 6 + 01)^{10}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} &:= (2-5-9+3-7-4+24+6+01)^{10} &:= (2-5-9+3+7-42-4+60-1)^{10} \\ &:= (-25+9+3-7+42-4-6-01)^{10} &:= (-2+5-9+3-7-42+4+60-1)^{10} \\ &:= (25+9+3+7-42+4+6-01)^{10} &:= (-2+5+9-3+7+42+4+60-1)^5 \\ &:= (-25-9-3+7+42+4-6+01)^{10} &:= (2-5+9+3+7+42+4+60-1)^5 \\ &:= (25+9-3+7+4-24-6-01)^{10} &:= (2-5+9-3-7-42-4+60+1)^{10} \\ &:= (25-9+3+7+4-24+6-01)^{10} &:= (-2+5+9+3+7+42-4+60+1)^5 \\ &:= (25+9+3+7-4-24-6+01)^{10} &:= (2+5-9-3-7-42+4+60+1)^{10} \\ &:= (-25+9-3+7+4+24-6+01)^{10} &:= (-2-5-9-3+7-42+4+60+1)^{10} \\ &:= (25+9-3-7+4-24+6+01)^{10} &:= (-2-5-9+3-7-4-24+60-1)^{10} \\ &:= (-25-9+3+7+4+24+6+01)^{10} &:= (2-5-9-3-7-4-24+60+1)^{10} \\ &:= (-25-9-3+7-4-2+46+01)^{10} &:= (25-93+74+2-4+6+01)^{10} \\ &:= (-25-9+3-7+4-2+46+01)^{10} &:= (25-9-3-7-42+46+01)^{10} \\ &:= (-25-9+3-7-4-2-4+60-1)^{10} &:= (25-9+3+7+42+4-60-1)^{10} \\ &:= (-25-9-3-7-4+2-4+60+1)^{10} &:= (25+9-3-7+42-4+60-1)^5 \\ &:= (-2+59-37+4-2-4-6-01)^{10} &:= (25+9-3-7+42+4-60+1)^{10} \\ &:= (2+59-37-4+2-4-6-01)^{10} &:= (-25+9-3+7-42+4+60+1)^{10} \\ &:= (-2+59-37-4-2+4-6-01)^{10} &:= (25+9+3+7+4+24-60-1)^{10} \\ &:= (-2+59+3+74-2-4-6-01)^5 &:= (-25+9+3-7-4-24+60-1)^{10} \\ &:= (2-59+3+74+2-4-6-01)^{10} &:= (-25-9-3+7+4-24+60+1)^{10} \\ &:= (-2-59+3+74-2+4-6-01)^{10} &:= (2-59+37+42-4-6-01)^{10} \\ &:= (2+59-3+74-2-4-6+01)^5 &:= (2+59+37+4+24-6+01)^5 \\ &:= (-2+59-3+74+2-4-6+01)^5 &:= (2+59-37+4-24+6+01)^{10} \\ &:= (2-59-3+74-2+4-6+01)^{10} &:= (-2+59+37-4+24+6+01)^5 \\ &:= (-2-59-3+74+2+4-6+01)^{10} &:= (-2-59+37+4+24+6+01)^{10} \\ &:= (-2-59-3+74-2-4+6+01)^{10} &:= (2+59+3+74-24+6+01)^5 \\ &:= (2-5+93-74-2+4-6-01)^{10} &:= (-2+59-3-74+24+6+01)^{10} \\ &:= (-2-5+93-74+2+4-6-01)^{10} &:= (-2+5+93+74-2-46-01)^5 \\ &:= (-2-5+93-74-2-4+6-01)^{10} &:= (2-5+93+74+2-46+01)^5 \\ &:= (-2+5+93-74-2-4-6+01)^{10} &:= (2+5+93+74+2+4-60+1)^5 \\ &:= (-2+5+9-3+7+42-46-01)^{10} &:= (259+3-74-2-4-60-1)^5 \\ &:= (2-5+9+3+7+42-46-01)^{10} &:= (259-3-74+2-4-60+1)^5 \\ &:= (-2+5+9+3-7-42+46-01)^{10} &:= (-25+93-74+24-6-01)^{10} \\ &:= (2+5-9+3+7-42+46-01)^{10} &:= (-25-93+74-2-4+60+1)^{10} \\ &:= (2+5+9-3-7-42+46+01)^{10} &:= (2+593-7-4-2-460-1)^5 \\ &:= (-2-5+9-3+7-42+46+01)^{10} &:= (-2+593-7-4+2-460-1)^5 \\ &:= (2+5+9+3+7+42+4-60-1)^{10} &:= (2+593+7+4+2+4-601)^{10} \\ &:= (-2-5+9+3-7-42-4+60-1)^{10} &:= (-2-593+7+4-2-4+601)^{10} \\ &:= (-2+5-9-3+7-42-4+60-1)^{10} &:= (2-593+7-4+2-4+601)^{10} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 & := (-2 - 593 + 7 - 4 - 2 + 4 + 601)^{10} & := (-2 + 611 - 5 + 85 - 281 - 6)^4 \\
 & := (2 + 59 + 37 - 42 - 46 + 01)^{10} & := (261 + 158 - 5 - 28 + 16)^4 \\
 & := (2 + 59 - 37 + 42 - 4 + 60 - 1)^5 & := (2 + 6 + 1158 + 52 - 816)^4 \\
 & := (2 - 59 - 37 + 42 + 4 + 60 - 1)^{10} & \mathbf{26198073000} := (-2 + 6 - 19 - 8 - 07 + 3000)^3 \\
 & := (2 + 59 - 37 + 42 + 4 - 60 + 1)^{10} & := (-26 - 19 + 8 + 07 + 3000)^3 \\
 & := (2 + 59 + 37 - 42 + 4 + 60 + 1)^5 & \mathbf{26277541317} := (2627 - 75 + 413 + 1 + 7)^3 \\
 & := (2 - 59 + 37 - 4 - 24 + 60 - 1)^{10} & := (2627 - 7 - 5 + 41 + 317)^3 \\
 & := (2 + 59 + 37 - 4 - 24 - 60 + 1)^{10} & \mathbf{26304066424} := (-2 - 6 + 3040 - 6 - 6 - 42 - 4)^3 \\
 & := (-2 - 5 - 93 + 74 - 24 + 60 + 1)^{10} & := (-26 + 3040 - 6 - 6 - 4 - 24)^3 \\
 & := (-2 + 5 - 9 + 374 - 246 - 01)^5 & := (2630 + 406 - 64 - 2 + 4)^3 \\
 & := (-259 - 37 + 424 - 6 - 01)^5 & \mathbf{26330609375} := (2 - 63 + 3060 - 9 - 3 - 7 - 5)^3 \\
 & := (-259 - 3 - 74 - 2 + 460 - 1)^5 & \mathbf{26376683281} := (2 + 63 + 7 + 6 + 6 - 8 + 328 - 1)^4 \\
 & := (25 + 9 - 374 + 2 + 460 - 1)^5 & := (-2 + 63 + 7 + 6 - 6 + 8 + 328 - 1)^4 \\
 & := (-2 + 593 - 7 + 4 + 24 - 601)^{10} & := (-2 + 63 + 7 - 6 + 6 + 8 + 328 - 1)^4 \\
 & := (2593 - 7 - 4 - 2460 - 1)^5 & := (-2 + 63 - 7 + 6 + 6 + 8 + 328 + 1)^4 \\
 & := (-259 - 37 - 42 + 460 - 1)^5 & := (-2 + 6 + 376 + 6 - 8 + 32 - 8 + 1)^4 \\
 \mathbf{25960629681} & := (2 - 5 + 9 - 6 - 06 + 2968 - 1)^3 & := (2 + 6 + 3 + 7 + 66 - 8 + 328 - 1)^4 \\
 & := (-2 + 5 - 9 + 6 - 06 + 2968 - 1)^3 & := (-2 - 6 + 3 + 7 + 66 + 8 + 328 - 1)^4 \\
 & := (-2 + 5 - 9 - 6 + 06 + 2968 - 1)^3 & := (-2 + 6 + 3 - 7 + 66 + 8 + 328 + 1)^4 \\
 \mathbf{26092364696} & := (2609 + 2 + 364 + 6 - 9 - 6)^3 & := (2 - 6 - 3 + 7 + 66 + 8 + 328 + 1)^4 \\
 & := (2609 + 2 + 364 - 6 - 9 + 6)^3 & := (-2 + 6 + 3 + 7 - 6 + 68 + 328 - 1)^4 \\
 & := (2 + 609 + 2364 + 6 - 9 - 6)^3 & := (-2 - 6 + 3 + 7 + 6 + 68 + 328 - 1)^4 \\
 & := (2 + 609 + 2364 - 6 - 9 + 6)^3 & := (2 + 6 - 3 + 7 - 6 + 68 + 328 + 1)^4 \\
 \mathbf{26115852816} & := (261 + 1 + 58 + 5 + 2 + 81 - 6)^4 & := (-2 + 6 + 3 - 7 + 6 + 68 + 328 + 1)^4 \\
 & := (261 - 1 + 58 - 5 + 2 + 81 + 6)^4 & := (2 - 6 - 3 + 7 + 6 + 68 + 328 + 1)^4 \\
 & := (261 + 1 + 5 + 8 + 52 + 81 - 6)^4 & := (263 + 76 + 68 + 3 + 2 - 8 - 1)^4 \\
 & := (261 - 1 - 5 + 8 + 52 + 81 + 6)^4 & := (263 + 7 + 6 + 6 + 8 + 32 + 81)^4 \\
 & := (2 + 61 + 1 + 58 + 5 + 281 - 6)^4 & := (-26 + 376 + 6 + 8 + 32 + 8 - 1)^4 \\
 & := (2 + 61 - 1 + 58 - 5 + 281 + 6)^4 & := (26 + 3 + 76 + 6 + 8 + 3 + 281)^4 \\
 & := (-2 + 6 - 115 - 8 + 528 - 1 - 6)^4 & := (26 - 3 - 7 + 66 - 8 + 328 + 1)^4 \\
 & := (-2 - 6 - 115 - 8 + 528 - 1 + 6)^4 & := (-2 - 6 + 376 - 6 - 8 - 32 + 81)^4 \\
 & := (261 + 158 + 5 + 2 - 8 - 16)^4 & := (2 + 6 + 37 + 66 + 8 + 3 + 281)^4 \\
 & := (-261 + 1 + 585 + 2 + 81 - 6)^4 & := (2 + 6 + 37 + 6 + 68 + 3 + 281)^4 \\
 & := (-26 - 115 + 8 + 528 + 1 + 6)^4 & := (26 + 37 - 6 + 68 - 3 + 281)^4 \\
 & := (26 + 11 + 5 + 85 + 281 - 6)^4 & := (-2 + 637 - 66 - 83 - 2 - 81)^4 \\
 & := (26 + 1 - 158 + 528 - 1 + 6)^4 & := (2 + 6 + 376 + 68 + 32 - 81)^4 \\
 & := (26 - 1 - 158 + 528 + 1 + 6)^4 & := (-2 + 6 - 3 + 766 - 83 - 281)^4 \\
 & := (26 + 1 + 15 + 85 + 281 - 6)^4 & := (263 - 76 - 68 + 3 + 281)^4
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 \mathbf{26490242141} &:= (-2 - 64 + 902 + 4 + 2141)^3 & &:= (-2 + 7 + 02 + 70 + 8 - 1 + 6 + 32)^5 \\
 \mathbf{26639462656} &:= (-2 + 6 - 6 - 39 + 462 - 6 - 5 - 6)^4 & &:= (27 + 027 + 08 - 1 + 63 - 2)^5 \\
 &:= (-2 - 6 + 6 - 39 + 462 - 6 - 5 - 6)^4 & &:= (27 + 02 + 70 + 8 + 16 - 3 + 2)^5 \\
 &:= (-2 - 6 - 6 - 39 + 462 + 6 - 5 - 6)^4 & &:= (2 + 70 + 27 + 08 + 16 - 3 + 2)^5 \\
 &:= (-2 - 6 - 6 - 39 + 462 - 6 - 5 + 6)^4 & &:= (2 + 70 + 2 - 7 + 081 + 6 - 32)^5 \\
 &:= (-2 + 6 + 6 + 3 - 9 + 462 - 6 - 56)^4 & &:= (2 - 7 + 02 + 70 + 81 + 6 - 32)^5 \\
 &:= (-2 + 6 - 6 - 3 + 9 + 462 - 6 - 56)^4 & &:= (270 + 2 - 70 - 81 + 6 - 3 - 2)^5 \\
 &:= (-2 - 6 + 6 - 3 + 9 + 462 - 6 - 56)^4 & &:= (270 - 2 - 70 - 81 + 6 - 3 + 2)^5 \\
 &:= (-2 + 6 - 6 + 3 - 9 + 462 + 6 - 56)^4 & &:= (270 + 2 + 7 + 08 - 163 - 2)^5 \\
 &:= (-2 - 6 + 6 + 3 - 9 + 462 + 6 - 56)^4 & &:= (270 - 2 + 7 + 08 - 163 + 2)^5 \\
 &:= (-2 - 6 - 6 - 3 + 9 + 462 + 6 - 56)^4 & &:= (2 - 702 + 7 + 0816 - 3 + 2)^5 \\
 &:= (-266 - 3 + 9 + 4 + 6 - 2 + 656)^4 & &:= (2 - 70 + 270 - 81 + 6 - 3 - 2)^5 \\
 &:= (-26 - 6 + 394 - 6 - 2 - 6 + 56)^4 & &:= (-2 - 70 + 270 - 81 + 6 - 3 + 2)^5 \\
 &:= (-26 + 6 + 3 + 9 + 462 + 6 - 56)^4 & &:= (2 + 7 + 0270 + 8 - 163 - 2)^5 \\
 &:= (2 + 66 + 394 + 6 - 2 - 6 - 56)^4 & &:= (-2 + 7 + 0270 + 8 - 163 + 2)^5 \\
 &:= (-2 + 66 + 394 + 6 + 2 - 6 - 56)^4 & & \\
 &:= (2 + 66 + 394 - 6 - 2 + 6 - 56)^4 & & \\
 &:= (-2 + 66 + 394 - 6 + 2 + 6 - 56)^4 & & \\
 &:= (-2 + 6 + 6 + 394 + 62 - 6 - 56)^4 & & \\
 &:= (-2 + 6 - 6 + 394 + 62 + 6 - 56)^4 & & \\
 &:= (-2 - 6 + 6 + 394 + 62 + 6 - 56)^4 & & \\
 &:= (-2 + 6 + 6 + 394 - 62 + 6 + 56)^4 & & \\
 &:= (-2 - 6 - 6 + 394 - 6 - 26 + 56)^4 & & \\
 &:= (-266 + 39 + 4 + 626 - 5 + 6)^4 & & \\
 &:= (26 + 639 + 4 + 6 - 265 - 6)^4 & & \\
 &:= (26 + 639 + 4 - 6 - 265 + 6)^4 & & \\
 \mathbf{26754163489} &:= (2 + 67 + 5 + 4 + 163489)^2 & & \\
 \mathbf{26784575488} &:= (-2678 + 4 + 5754 - 88)^3 & & \\
 \mathbf{26904200625} &:= (2 + 6 - 90 + 420 + 062 + 5)^4 & & \\
 \mathbf{27027081632} &:= (27 + 02 + 7 + 081 + 6 - 3 + 2)^5 & & \\
 &:= (2 + 70 - 2 + 70 - 8 + 1 - 6 - 3 - 2)^5 & & \\
 &:= (-2 + 70 + 2 + 70 - 8 + 1 - 6 - 3 - 2)^5 & & \\
 &:= (-2 + 70 - 2 + 70 - 8 - 1 - 6 + 3 - 2)^5 & & \\
 &:= (-2 + 70 - 2 + 70 - 8 + 1 - 6 - 3 + 2)^5 & & \\
 &:= (2 + 70 - 2 + 7 + 08 - 1 + 6 + 32)^5 & & \\
 &:= (-2 + 70 + 2 + 7 + 08 - 1 + 6 + 32)^5 & & \\
 &:= (2 + 7 + 027 + 081 + 6 - 3 + 2)^5 & & \\
 &:= (2 + 7 - 02 + 70 + 8 - 1 + 6 + 32)^5 & & \\
 \mathbf{27135225125} &:= (-2 - 7 - 1 + 3522 - 512 + 5)^3 & & \\
 \mathbf{27162324216} &:= (2716 + 232 + 42 + 16)^3 & & \\
 \mathbf{27189441343} &:= (2718 - 9 - 44 - 1 + 343)^3 & & \\
 &:= (2718 - 9 - 4 - 41 + 343)^3 & & \\
 &:= (2 + 718 + 944 + 1343)^3 & & \\
 \mathbf{27298090331} &:= (27 + 2980 + 9 - 03 - 3 + 1)^3 & & \\
 &:= (-27 + 2980 + 90 - 33 + 1)^3 & & \\
 \mathbf{27379766744} &:= (-27 + 3797 - 6 - 6 - 744)^3 & & \\
 &:= (27 + 3797 - 66 - 744)^3 & & \\
 \mathbf{27434308096} &:= (2 - 74 - 3 - 4 + 3080 + 9 + 6)^3 & & \\
 &:= (27 + 4 - 3 + 4 + 3080 - 96)^3 & & \\
 \mathbf{27439591201} &:= (2 + 7 - 4 + 395 + 9 + 1 - 2 - 01)^4 & & \\
 &:= (-2 + 7 - 4 + 395 + 9 + 1 + 2 - 01)^4 & & \\
 &:= (2 + 7 - 4 + 395 + 9 - 1 - 2 + 01)^4 & & \\
 &:= (-2 + 7 - 4 + 395 + 9 - 1 + 2 + 01)^4 & & \\
 &:= (2 - 7 + 4 + 395 + 9 + 1 + 2 + 01)^4 & & \\
 &:= (27 - 4 + 395 - 9 + 1 - 2 - 01)^4 & & \\
 &:= (27 - 4 + 395 - 9 - 1 - 2 + 01)^4 & & \\
 &:= (2 - 7 + 439 - 5 - 9 - 12 - 01)^4 & & \\
 &:= (-2 + 7 - 4 + 395 - 9 + 1 + 20 - 1)^4 & & \\
 &:= (-2 + 7 - 4 + 395 - 9 - 1 + 20 + 1)^4 & & \\
 &:= (2 - 7 + 4 + 395 - 9 + 1 + 20 + 1)^4 & & \\
 &:= (27 + 439 - 59 - 1 + 2 - 01)^4 & &
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} &:= (27 + 439 - 59 + 1 - 2 + 01)^4 &:= (27 + 5 - 1 - 2 + 6 - 1 - 4 + 1 - 1 + 1)^7 \\ &:= (27 - 4 + 395 + 9 + 1 - 20 - 1)^4 &:= (27 + 5 - 1 + 2 - 6 - 1 + 4 + 1 - 1 + 1)^7 \\ &:= (27 - 4 + 395 + 9 - 1 - 20 + 1)^4 &:= (27 - 5 + 1 - 2 + 6 - 1 + 4 + 1 - 1 + 1)^7 \\ &:= (-2 - 74 + 395 + 91 - 2 - 01)^4 &:= (27 + 5 + 1 - 2 - 6 + 1 + 4 + 1 - 1 + 1)^7 \\ &:= (2 + 7 + 439 - 59 - 1 + 20 - 1)^4 &:= (27 - 5 - 1 - 2 + 6 + 1 + 4 + 1 - 1 + 1)^7 \\ &:= (-2 + 7 + 439 - 59 + 1 + 20 + 1)^4 &:= (27 + 5 - 1 - 2 + 6 - 1 - 4 - 1 + 1 + 1)^7 \\ &:= (2 + 7 - 4 + 3 + 9 + 591 - 201)^4 &:= (27 + 5 - 1 + 2 - 6 - 1 + 4 - 1 + 1 + 1)^7 \\ &:= (27 - 4 - 3 + 95 + 91 + 201)^4 &:= (27 - 5 + 1 - 2 + 6 - 1 + 4 - 1 + 1 + 1)^7 \\ &:= (27 - 4 + 3 - 9 + 591 - 201)^4 &:= (27 + 5 + 1 - 2 - 6 + 1 + 4 - 1 + 1 + 1)^7 \\ \mathbf{27512614111} &:= (2 + 7 + 5 + 1 + 2 + 6 + 1 + 4 + 1 + 1 + 1)^7 &:= (27 - 5 - 1 - 2 + 6 + 1 + 4 - 1 + 1 + 1)^7 \\ &:= (27 + 5 - 1 + 2 + 6 - 1 - 4 - 1 - 1 - 1)^7 &:= (27 - 5 + 1 + 2 + 6 + 1 - 4 + 1 + 1 + 1)^7 \\ &:= (27 + 5 + 1 - 2 + 6 + 1 - 4 - 1 - 1 - 1)^7 &:= (27 + 5 + 1 - 2 - 6 - 1 + 4 + 1 + 1 + 1)^7 \\ &:= (27 - 5 + 1 + 2 + 6 - 1 + 4 - 1 - 1 - 1)^7 &:= (27 - 5 - 1 - 2 + 6 - 1 + 4 + 1 + 1 + 1)^7 \\ &:= (27 + 5 + 1 + 2 - 6 + 1 + 4 - 1 - 1 - 1)^7 &:= (27 + 5 - 1 - 2 - 6 + 1 + 4 + 1 + 1 + 1)^7 \\ &:= (27 - 5 - 1 + 2 + 6 + 1 + 4 - 1 - 1 - 1)^7 &:= (2 + 7 + 5 - 1 + 26 - 1 - 4 - 1 - 1 - 1)^7 \\ &:= (27 + 5 + 1 - 2 + 6 - 1 - 4 + 1 - 1 - 1)^7 &:= (-2 + 7 + 5 + 1 + 26 + 1 - 4 - 1 - 1 - 1)^7 \\ &:= (27 + 5 - 1 - 2 + 6 + 1 - 4 + 1 - 1 - 1)^7 &:= (2 + 7 - 5 + 1 + 26 - 1 + 4 - 1 - 1 - 1)^7 \\ &:= (27 + 5 + 1 + 2 - 6 - 1 + 4 + 1 - 1 - 1)^7 &:= (2 + 7 - 5 - 1 + 26 + 1 + 4 - 1 - 1 - 1)^7 \\ &:= (27 - 5 - 1 + 2 + 6 - 1 + 4 + 1 - 1 - 1)^7 &:= (-2 + 7 + 5 + 1 + 26 - 1 - 4 + 1 - 1 - 1)^7 \\ &:= (27 + 5 - 1 + 2 - 6 + 1 + 4 + 1 - 1 - 1)^7 &:= (-2 + 7 + 5 - 1 + 26 + 1 - 4 + 1 - 1 - 1)^7 \\ &:= (27 - 5 + 1 - 2 + 6 + 1 + 4 + 1 - 1 - 1)^7 &:= (2 + 7 - 5 - 1 + 26 - 1 + 4 + 1 - 1 - 1)^7 \\ &:= (27 + 5 + 1 - 2 + 6 - 1 - 4 - 1 + 1 - 1)^7 &:= (-2 + 7 - 5 + 1 + 26 + 1 + 4 + 1 - 1 - 1)^7 \\ &:= (27 + 5 - 1 - 2 + 6 + 1 - 4 - 1 + 1 - 1)^7 &:= (2 - 7 + 5 + 1 + 26 + 1 + 4 + 1 - 1 - 1)^7 \\ &:= (27 + 5 + 1 + 2 - 6 - 1 + 4 - 1 + 1 - 1)^7 &:= (-2 + 7 + 5 + 1 + 26 - 1 - 4 - 1 + 1 - 1)^7 \\ &:= (27 - 5 - 1 + 2 + 6 - 1 + 4 - 1 + 1 - 1)^7 &:= (-2 + 7 + 5 - 1 + 26 + 1 - 4 - 1 + 1 - 1)^7 \\ &:= (27 + 5 - 1 + 2 - 6 + 1 + 4 - 1 + 1 - 1)^7 &:= (2 + 7 - 5 - 1 + 26 - 1 + 4 - 1 + 1 - 1)^7 \\ &:= (27 - 5 + 1 - 2 + 6 + 1 + 4 - 1 + 1 - 1)^7 &:= (-2 + 7 - 5 + 1 + 26 + 1 + 4 - 1 + 1 - 1)^7 \\ &:= (27 + 5 - 1 - 2 + 6 - 1 - 4 + 1 + 1 - 1)^7 &:= (2 - 7 + 5 + 1 + 26 + 1 + 4 - 1 + 1 - 1)^7 \\ &:= (27 + 5 - 1 + 2 - 6 - 1 + 4 + 1 + 1 - 1)^7 &:= (-2 + 7 + 5 - 1 + 26 - 1 - 4 + 1 + 1 - 1)^7 \\ &:= (27 - 5 + 1 - 2 + 6 - 1 + 4 + 1 + 1 - 1)^7 &:= (-2 + 7 - 5 + 1 + 26 - 1 + 4 + 1 + 1 - 1)^7 \\ &:= (27 + 5 + 1 - 2 - 6 + 1 + 4 + 1 + 1 - 1)^7 &:= (2 - 7 + 5 + 1 + 26 - 1 + 4 + 1 + 1 - 1)^7 \\ &:= (27 - 5 - 1 - 2 + 6 + 1 + 4 + 1 + 1 - 1)^7 &:= (-2 + 7 - 5 - 1 + 26 + 1 + 4 + 1 + 1 - 1)^7 \\ &:= (27 + 5 + 1 - 2 + 6 - 1 - 4 - 1 - 1 + 1)^7 &:= (2 - 7 + 5 - 1 + 26 + 1 + 4 + 1 + 1 - 1)^7 \\ &:= (27 + 5 - 1 - 2 + 6 + 1 - 4 - 1 - 1 + 1)^7 &:= (-2 + 7 + 5 + 1 + 26 - 1 - 4 - 1 - 1 + 1)^7 \\ &:= (27 + 5 + 1 + 2 - 6 - 1 + 4 - 1 - 1 + 1)^7 &:= (-2 + 7 + 5 - 1 + 26 + 1 - 4 - 1 - 1 + 1)^7 \\ &:= (27 - 5 - 1 + 2 + 6 - 1 + 4 - 1 - 1 + 1)^7 &:= (2 + 7 - 5 - 1 + 26 - 1 + 4 - 1 - 1 + 1)^7 \\ &:= (27 + 5 - 1 + 2 - 6 + 1 + 4 - 1 - 1 + 1)^7 &:= (-2 + 7 - 5 + 1 + 26 + 1 + 4 - 1 - 1 + 1)^7 \\ &:= (27 - 5 + 1 - 2 + 6 + 1 + 4 - 1 - 1 + 1)^7 &:= (2 - 7 + 5 + 1 + 26 + 1 + 4 - 1 - 1 + 1)^7 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} & := (-2+7+5-1+26-1-4+1-1+1)^7 & := (2-7-5+1+2-6+1+41+1+1)^7 \\ & := (-2+7-5+1+26-1+4+1-1+1)^7 & := (-27+5+1-2+61-4-1-1-1)^7 \\ & := (2-7+5+1+26-1+4+1-1+1)^7 & := (-27-5-1+2+61+4-1-1-1)^7 \\ & := (-2+7-5-1+26+1+4+1-1+1)^7 & := (-27+5-1-2+61-4+1-1-1)^7 \\ & := (2-7+5-1+26+1+4+1-1+1)^7 & := (-27-5+1-2+61+4+1-1-1)^7 \\ & := (-2+7+5-1+26-1-4-1+1+1)^7 & := (-27+5-1-2+61-4-1+1-1)^7 \\ & := (-2+7-5+1+26-1+4-1+1+1)^7 & := (-27-5+1-2+61+4-1+1-1)^7 \\ & := (2-7+5+1+26-1+4-1+1+1)^7 & := (-27-5-1-2+61+4+1+1-1)^7 \\ & := (-2+7-5-1+26+1+4-1+1+1)^7 & := (-27+5-1-2+61-4-1-1+1)^7 \\ & := (2-7+5-1+26+1+4-1+1+1)^7 & := (-27-5+1-2+61+4-1-1+1)^7 \\ & := (2+7-5+1+26+1-4+1+1+1)^7 & := (-27-5-1-2+61+4+1-1+1)^7 \\ & := (-2+7-5-1+26-1+4+1+1+1)^7 & := (-27-5-1-2+61+4-1+1+1)^7 \\ & := (2-7+5-1+26-1+4+1+1+1)^7 & := (-27-5+1+2+61-4+1+1+1)^7 \\ & := (-2-7+5+1+26+1+4+1+1+1)^7 & := (-27+5+1+2+6+1+41+1+1)^7 \\ & := (-2+7-5+1-2-6-1+41-1-1)^7 & := (-2+7+51-2-6-14-1-1-1)^7 \\ & := (2-7+5+1-2-6-1+41-1-1)^7 & := (-2-7+51-2+6-14+1-1-1)^7 \\ & := (-2-7+5+1+2-6-1+41-1-1)^7 & := (-2-7+51-2+6-14-1+1-1)^7 \\ & := (2-7-5-1-2+6-1+41-1-1)^7 & := (-2-7+51-2+6-14-1-1+1)^7 \\ & := (-2-7-5-1+2+6-1+41-1-1)^7 & := (2-7+51+2-6-14+1+1+1)^7 \\ & := (-2+7-5-1-2-6+1+41-1-1)^7 & := (-2+7+51-2-6-1-4-11-1)^7 \\ & := (2-7+5-1-2-6+1+41-1-1)^7 & := (-2-7+51-2+6+1-4-11-1)^7 \\ & := (-2-7+5-1+2-6+1+41-1-1)^7 & := (2-7+51-2-6+1+4-11-1)^7 \\ & := (-2-7-5+1-2+6+1+41-1-1)^7 & := (-2-7+51+2-6+1+4-11-1)^7 \\ & := (-2+7-5-1-2-6-1+41+1-1)^7 & := (-2-7+51-2+6-1-4-11+1)^7 \\ & := (2-7+5-1-2-6-1+41+1-1)^7 & := (2-7+51-2-6-1+4-11+1)^7 \\ & := (-2-7+5-1+2-6-1+41+1-1)^7 & := (-2-7+51+2-6-1+4-11+1)^7 \\ & := (-2-7-5+1-2+6-1+41+1-1)^7 & := (-2+7+51-2-6-1-4-1-11)^7 \\ & := (-2-7+5+1-2-6+1+41+1-1)^7 & := (-2-7+51-2+6+1-4-1-11)^7 \\ & := (-2-7-5-1-2+6+1+41+1-1)^7 & := (2-7+51-2-6+1+4-1-11)^7 \\ & := (-2+7-5-1-2-6-1+41-1+1)^7 & := (-2-7+51+2-6+1+4-1-11)^7 \\ & := (2-7+5-1-2-6-1+41-1+1)^7 & := (-2-7+51-2+6-1-4+1-11)^7 \\ & := (-2-7+5-1+2-6-1+41-1+1)^7 & := (2-7+51-2-6-1+4+1-11)^7 \\ & := (-2-7-5+1-2+6-1+41-1+1)^7 & := (-2-7+51+2-6-1+4+1-11)^7 \\ & := (-2-7+5+1-2-6+1+41-1+1)^7 & := (2+7+5+12-6+14-1-1-1)^7 \\ & := (-2-7-5-1-2+6+1+41-1+1)^7 & := (-2+7-5+12+6+14+1-1-1)^7 \\ & := (-2-7+5+1-2-6-1+41+1+1)^7 & := (2-7+5+12+6+14+1-1-1)^7 \\ & := (-2-7-5-1-2+6-1+41+1+1)^7 & := (-2+7-5+12+6+14-1+1-1)^7 \\ & := (-2-7+5-1-2-6+1+41+1+1)^7 & := (2-7+5+12+6+14-1+1-1)^7 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} & := (-2+7+5+12-6+14+1+1-1)^7 & := (-2-7+5+1+2+6+14+11+1)^7 \\ & := (-2+7-5+12+6+14-1-1+1)^7 & := (2+7+5+1-2-6+14-1+11)^7 \\ & := (2-7+5+12+6+14-1-1+1)^7 & := (-2+7+5+1+2-6+14-1+11)^7 \\ & := (-2+7+5+12-6+14+1-1+1)^7 & := (2+7-5-1-2+6+14-1+11)^7 \\ & := (-2+7+5+12-6+14-1+1+1)^7 & := (-2+7-5-1+2+6+14-1+11)^7 \\ & := (-2-7+5+12+6+14+1+1+1)^7 & := (2-7+5-1+2+6+14-1+11)^7 \\ & := (-2+7-5+12+6-1+4+11-1)^7 & := (2+7+5-1-2-6+14+1+11)^7 \\ & := (2-7+5+12+6-1+4+11-1)^7 & := (-2+7+5-1+2-6+14+1+11)^7 \\ & := (-2+7+5+12-6+1+4+11-1)^7 & := (-2+7-5+1-2+6+14+1+11)^7 \\ & := (2+7-5+12+6+1-4+11+1)^7 & := (2-7+5+1-2+6+14+1+11)^7 \\ & := (-2+7+5+12-6-1+4+11+1)^7 & := (-2-7+5+1+2+6+14+1+11)^7 \\ & := (-2-7+5+12+6+1+4+11+1)^7 & := (-27+51+2-6+14-1-1-1)^7 \\ & := (-2+7-5+12+6-1+4-1+11)^7 & := (-27+51-2-6+14+1+1-1)^7 \\ & := (2-7+5+12+6-1+4-1+11)^7 & := (-27+51-2-6+14+1-1+1)^7 \\ & := (-2+7+5+12-6+1+4-1+11)^7 & := (-27+51-2-6+14-1+1+1)^7 \\ & := (2+7-5+12+6+1-4+1+11)^7 & := (-27+51-2-6+1+4+11-1)^7 \\ & := (-2+7+5+12-6-1+4+1+11)^7 & := (-27+51-2-6-1+4+11+1)^7 \\ & := (-2-7+5+12+6+1+4+1+11)^7 & := (-27+51-2-6+1+4-1+11)^7 \\ & := (2+7+5+1-26+1+41+1-1)^7 & := (-27+51-2-6-1+4+1+11)^7 \\ & := (2+7+5+1-26+1+41-1+1)^7 & := (27-5-12+6+14+1+1-1)^7 \\ & := (2+7+5+1-26-1+41+1+1)^7 & := (27-5-12+6+14+1-1+1)^7 \\ & := (2+7+5-1-26+1+41+1+1)^7 & := (27-5-12+6+14-1+1+1)^7 \\ & := (2+7+5+1-2+61-41-1-1)^7 & := (27+5-12-6+14+1+1+1)^7 \\ & := (-2+7+5+1+2+61-41-1-1)^7 & := (27-5+12+6-1+4-11-1)^7 \\ & := (2+7+5-1-2+61-41+1-1)^7 & := (27+5+12-6+1+4-11-1)^7 \\ & := (-2+7+5-1+2+61-41+1-1)^7 & := (27+5-12+6-1-4+11-1)^7 \\ & := (2+7+5-1-2+61-41-1+1)^7 & := (27-5-12+6+1+4+11-1)^7 \\ & := (-2+7+5-1+2+61-41-1+1)^7 & := (27+5+12-6-1+4-11+1)^7 \\ & := (-2+7+5+1-2+61-41+1+1)^7 & := (27-5-12+6-1+4+11+1)^7 \\ & := (2+7+5+1-2-6+14+11-1)^7 & := (27+5-12-6+1+4+11+1)^7 \\ & := (-2+7+5+1+2-6+14+11-1)^7 & := (27-5+12+6-1+4-1-11)^7 \\ & := (2+7-5-1-2+6+14+11-1)^7 & := (27+5+12-6+1+4-1-11)^7 \\ & := (-2+7-5-1+2+6+14+11-1)^7 & := (27+5+12-6-1+4+1-11)^7 \\ & := (2-7+5-1+2+6+14+11-1)^7 & := (27+5-12+6-1-4-1+11)^7 \\ & := (2+7+5-1-2-6+14+11+1)^7 & := (27-5-12+6+1+4-1+11)^7 \\ & := (-2+7+5-1+2-6+14+11+1)^7 & := (27-5-12+6-1+4+1+11)^7 \\ & := (-2+7-5+1-2+6+14+11+1)^7 & := (27+5-12-6+1+4+1+11)^7 \\ & := (2-7+5+1-2+6+14+11+1)^7 & := (-27-5-1+26-1+41-1-1)^7 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} &:= (27+5+1+2-6+14-11-1)^7 & &:= (-2-7+51-26+14+1-1+1)^7 \\ &:= (27-5-1+2+6+14-11-1)^7 & &:= (-2-7+51-26+14-1+1+1)^7 \\ &:= (27+5-1-2+6-14+11-1)^7 & &:= (-2-7+51-26+1+4+11-1)^7 \\ &:= (27+5-1+2-6+14-11+1)^7 & &:= (-2-7+51-26-1+4+11+1)^7 \\ &:= (27-5+1-2+6+14-11+1)^7 & &:= (-2-7+51-26+1+4-1+11)^7 \\ &:= (27+5+1+2-6+14-1-11)^7 & &:= (-2-7+51-26-1+4+1+11)^7 \\ &:= (27-5-1+2+6+14-1-11)^7 & &:= (2+7-51-2+61+4+11-1)^7 \\ &:= (27+5-1+2-6+14+1-11)^7 & &:= (-2+7-51+2+61+4+11-1)^7 \\ &:= (27-5+1-2+6+14+1-11)^7 & &:= (2+7-51-2+61+4-1+11)^7 \\ &:= (27+5-1-2+6-14-1+11)^7 & &:= (-2+7-51+2+61+4-1+11)^7 \\ &:= (2+75+12-61+4+1-1-1)^7 & &:= (-2+7+51-2+6+1-41+11)^7 \\ &:= (2+75+12-61+4-1+1-1)^7 & &:= (2-7-5-12+61+4-11-1)^7 \\ &:= (2+75+12-61+4-1-1+1)^7 & &:= (-2-7+5-12+61-4-11+1)^7 \\ &:= (-2+75+12-61+4+1+1+1)^7 & &:= (2-7-5-12+61+4-1-11)^7 \\ &:= (2+75-12+6+1-41+1-1)^7 & &:= (-2-7+5-12+61-4+1-11)^7 \\ &:= (2+75-12+6+1-41-1+1)^7 & &:= (-2-7+5+12-6-1+41-11)^7 \\ &:= (2+75-12+6-1-41+1+1)^7 & &:= (-2-7-5-12+6-1+41+11)^7 \\ &:= (-2+75+1-26-14-1-1-1)^7 & &:= (-2-7+5-12-6+1+41+11)^7 \\ &:= (-2+75-1-26-14+1-1-1)^7 & &:= (2+7-5-1+26+14-11-1)^7 \\ &:= (-2+75-1-26-14-1+1-1)^7 & &:= (-2+7+5-1+26-14+11-1)^7 \\ &:= (-2+75-1-26-14-1-1+1)^7 & &:= (-2+7-5+1+26+14-11+1)^7 \\ &:= (-2+75+1-26-1-4-11-1)^7 & &:= (2-7+5+1+26+14-11+1)^7 \\ &:= (-2+75-1-26+1-4-11-1)^7 & &:= (2+7-5-1+26+14-1-11)^7 \\ &:= (-2+75-1-26-1-4-11+1)^7 & &:= (-2+7-5+1+26+14+1-11)^7 \\ &:= (-2+75+1-26-1-4-1-11)^7 & &:= (2-7+5+1+26+14+1-11)^7 \\ &:= (-2+75-1-26+1-4-1-11)^7 & &:= (-2+7+5-1+26-14-1+11)^7 \\ &:= (-2+75-1-26-1-4+1-11)^7 & &:= (-2-7-5+1-2-61-4+111)^7 \\ &:= (2+75-1+2-61+4+11-1)^7 & &:= (27-51+2+61+4-11-1)^7 \\ &:= (2+75+1-2-61+4+11+1)^7 & &:= (27+51-2-61+4+11+1)^7 \\ &:= (-2+75+1+2-61+4+11+1)^7 & &:= (27-51+2+61+4-1-11)^7 \\ &:= (2+75-1+2-61+4-1+11)^7 & &:= (27+51-2-61+4+1+11)^7 \\ &:= (2+75+1-2-61+4+1+11)^7 & &:= (27+51-2+6+1-41-11)^7 \\ &:= (-2+75+1+2-61+4+1+11)^7 & &:= (27-51-2+6-1+41+11)^7 \\ &:= (2+75-1+2+6-1-41-11)^7 & &:= (-27-5-12+61+4+11-1)^7 \\ &:= (2+75+1-2+6+1-41-11)^7 & &:= (-27-5-12+61+4-1+11)^7 \\ &:= (-2+75+1+2+6+1-41-11)^7 & &:= (27+5-1+26-14-11-1)^7 \\ &:= (2-7+51-26+14-1-1-1)^7 & &:= (27+5+1-26+14+11-1)^7 \\ &:= (-2-7+51-26+14+1+1-1)^7 & &:= (27+5-1-26+14+11+1)^7 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 &:= (-27 + 5 + 1 + 26 + 14 + 11 + 1)^7 \\
 &:= (27 + 5 - 1 + 26 - 14 - 1 - 11)^7 \\
 &:= (27 + 5 + 1 - 26 + 14 - 1 + 11)^7 \\
 &:= (27 + 5 - 1 - 26 + 14 + 1 + 11)^7 \\
 &:= (-27 + 5 + 1 + 26 + 14 + 1 + 11)^7 \\
 &:= (-27 + 5 + 1 - 2 - 61 + 4 + 111)^7 \\
 &:= (-2 + 75 - 12 - 6 - 14 - 11 + 1)^7 \\
 &:= (-2 + 75 - 12 - 6 - 14 + 1 - 11)^7 \\
 &:= (-2 - 75 - 12 + 6 - 1 + 4 + 111)^7 \\
 &:= (2 - 75 - 1 + 2 + 6 - 14 + 111)^7 \\
 &:= (-2 + 7 + 51 + 26 + 1 - 41 - 11)^7 \\
 &:= (-2 + 7 - 51 + 26 - 1 + 41 + 11)^7 \\
 &:= (2 + 7 + 51 + 2 - 61 + 41 - 11)^7 \\
 &:= (-2 - 7 + 51 - 2 - 61 + 41 + 11)^7 \\
 &:= (2 + 7 + 5 - 126 + 141 + 1 + 1)^7 \\
 &:= (-2 + 7 + 5 + 12 + 61 - 41 - 11)^7 \\
 &:= (275 + 1 - 261 + 4 + 11 + 1)^7 \\
 &:= (275 + 1 - 261 + 4 + 1 + 11)^7 \\
 &:= (27 - 51 + 26 - 1 + 41 - 11)^7 \\
 &:= (-27 + 51 - 2 + 61 - 41 - 11)^7 \\
 &:= (-2 + 75 + 12 + 61 - 4 - 111)^7 \\
 &:= (27 + 5 - 126 + 14 + 111)^7 \\
 \mathbf{27625773167} &:= (-2 - 76 - 2 - 57 - 7 + 3167)^3 \\
 &:= (2 - 76 + 2 + 5 - 77 + 3167)^3 \\
 &:= (-2762 + 5773 - 1 + 6 + 7)^3 \\
 &:= (276 + 2577 + 3 + 167)^3 \\
 \mathbf{27680640625} &:= (-2 + 76 - 8 + 06 - 4 - 06 - 2 - 5)^6 \\
 &:= (2 + 76 - 8 - 06 + 4 - 06 - 2 - 5)^6 \\
 &:= (-2 + 76 - 8 - 06 - 4 + 06 - 2 - 5)^6 \\
 &:= (-2 + 76 - 8 - 06 + 4 - 06 + 2 - 5)^6 \\
 &:= (2 + 76 + 8 + 06 - 40 + 6 + 2 - 5)^6 \\
 &:= (-2 + 76 - 80 + 64 - 06 - 2 + 5)^6 \\
 &:= (2 - 76 + 80 + 6 + 40 + 6 + 2 - 5)^6 \\
 &:= (2 + 76 - 80 - 6 - 4 + 062 + 5)^6 \\
 &:= (2 - 76 + 8 + 064 + 062 - 5)^6 \\
 &:= (-2 + 76 - 8 + 06 + 40 - 62 + 5)^6 \\
 &:= (-2 + 76 + 8 - 06 - 40 - 6 + 25)^6 \\
 &:= (2 + 76 - 8 + 06 - 40 - 6 + 25)^6
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 &:= (2 + 76 - 8 - 06 - 40 + 6 + 25)^6 \\
 &:= (2 + 76 + 80 - 6 - 40 - 62 + 5)^6 \\
 &:= (-2 - 76 + 80 - 6 + 40 - 6 + 25)^6 \\
 &:= (2 + 76 - 8 - 0640 + 625)^6 \\
 &:= (276 - 806 - 40 + 625)^6 \\
 \mathbf{27710263296} &:= (277 - 1 - 02 + 6 + 32 + 96)^4 \\
 &:= (2 + 77 + 10 + 2 - 6 + 329 - 6)^4 \\
 &:= (2 + 77 - 10 - 2 + 6 + 329 + 6)^4 \\
 &:= (-2 + 77 - 10 + 2 + 6 + 329 + 6)^4 \\
 &:= (-2 + 7 + 710 - 2 - 6 - 3 - 296)^4 \\
 &:= (2 - 7 + 710 + 2 - 6 + 3 - 296)^4 \\
 &:= (277 + 102 - 6 + 32 + 9 - 6)^4 \\
 &:= (277 + 10 + 26 - 3 + 2 + 96)^4 \\
 &:= (-2 + 771 - 0263 - 2 - 96)^4 \\
 &:= (-2 + 771 - 026 - 329 - 6)^4 \\
 &:= (-2 + 771 - 02 - 63 - 296)^4 \\
 &:= (2 + 77 + 10 + 26 - 3 + 296)^4 \\
 &:= (2 - 7 + 710 + 26 - 329 + 6)^4 \\
 &:= (277 - 102 - 63 + 296)^4 \\
 \mathbf{27735580683} &:= (-2773 + 5 + 5806 - 8 - 3)^3 \\
 \mathbf{27763077952} &:= (2 - 7 - 7 + 6 + 3077 + 9 - 52)^3 \\
 \mathbf{27928443304} &:= (2 + 7 + 9 - 284 - 4 + 3304)^3 \\
 &:= (27 - 9 - 284 - 4 + 3304)^3 \\
 \mathbf{27982932961} &:= (-2 + 7 + 9 + 82 - 9 + 329 - 6 - 1)^4 \\
 &:= (-2 + 7 - 9 + 82 + 9 + 329 - 6 - 1)^4 \\
 &:= (2 + 7 - 9 + 82 - 9 + 329 + 6 + 1)^4 \\
 &:= (-2 - 7 + 9 + 82 - 9 + 329 + 6 + 1)^4 \\
 &:= (-2 - 7 - 9 + 82 + 9 + 329 + 6 + 1)^4 \\
 &:= (2 + 7 + 9 + 82 + 9 + 3 + 296 + 1)^4 \\
 &:= (2 + 7 + 9 + 8 + 2 - 9 + 329 + 61)^4 \\
 &:= (2 - 7 + 9 + 8 - 2 + 9 + 329 + 61)^4 \\
 &:= (2 + 7 - 9 + 8 + 2 + 9 + 329 + 61)^4 \\
 &:= (-2 - 7 + 9 + 8 + 2 + 9 + 329 + 61)^4 \\
 &:= (279 + 82 + 9 + 3 + 29 + 6 + 1)^4 \\
 &:= (279 + 82 - 9 + 3 + 2 - 9 + 61)^4 \\
 &:= (279 - 8 + 2 + 9 + 32 + 96 - 1)^4 \\
 &:= (279 + 8 + 2 - 9 + 32 + 96 + 1)^4 \\
 &:= (-27 + 9 + 82 + 9 + 329 + 6 + 1)^4
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 &:= (27 + 9 + 82 - 9 + 3 + 296 + 1)^4 & &:= (2 + 8 - 15 + 30 + 5 + 6 + 84 + 3)^5 \\
 &:= (27 - 9 + 82 + 9 + 3 + 296 + 1)^4 & &:= (2 + 8 + 1 + 5 - 30 + 56 + 84 - 3)^5 \\
 &:= (27 + 9 + 8 + 293 + 2 + 9 + 61)^4 & &:= (-2 + 8 - 1 + 5 - 30 + 56 + 84 + 3)^5 \\
 &:= (27 + 9 + 8 + 29 + 329 + 6 + 1)^4 & &:= (-2 + 8 + 1 - 5 + 30 + 56 - 8 + 43)^5 \\
 &:= (27 - 9 + 8 + 2 - 9 + 329 + 61)^4 & &:= (-2 - 8 + 1 - 5 + 30 + 56 + 8 + 43)^5 \\
 &:= (2 + 7 + 9 + 8 + 293 + 29 + 61)^4 & &:= (28 - 15 + 30 + 5 + 68 + 4 + 3)^5 \\
 &:= (-2 - 7 - 9 + 8 + 29 + 329 + 61)^4 & &:= (28 - 15 + 30 + 5 - 6 + 84 - 3)^5 \\
 &:= (279 + 8 + 29 + 3 + 29 + 61)^4 & &:= (28 + 15 + 30 + 5 - 6 + 8 + 43)^5 \\
 &:= (27 - 9 + 8 + 293 + 29 + 61)^4 & &:= (28 - 15 + 3 + 056 + 8 + 43)^5 \\
 &:= (-27 + 9 + 8 + 29 + 329 + 61)^4 & &:= (2 + 81 + 5 + 30 + 56 - 8 - 43)^5 \\
 \mathbf{28094464000} &:= (-2 - 8 - 0944 - 6 + 4000)^3 & &:= (-2 - 8 + 153 + 05 - 68 + 43)^5 \\
 \mathbf{28122197921} &:= (2812 + 2 + 197 + 9 + 21)^3 & &:= (-28 + 15 + 30 - 5 + 68 + 43)^5 \\
 &:= (28 + 1 + 2219 + 792 + 1)^3 & &:= (-28 - 1 - 530 - 5 + 684 + 3)^5 \\
 &:= (2 + 812 + 2197 + 9 + 21)^3 & & \\
 &:= (2 - 81 + 2 + 2197 + 921)^3 & & \mathbf{28167580224} := (28 + 167580 + 224)^2 \\
 \mathbf{28153056843} &:= (28 + 1 + 5 - 3 + 05 + 6 + 84 - 3)^5 & & \mathbf{28177720507} := (2817 + 7 + 7 + 205 + 07)^3 \\
 &:= (28 + 1 + 5 + 3 + 05 - 6 + 84 + 3)^5 & & \mathbf{28233316125} := (-282 + 3331 - 6 - 1 - 2 + 5)^3 \\
 &:= (28 - 1 + 5 + 3 - 05 + 6 + 84 + 3)^5 & & &:= (-282 + 3 + 3316 + 1 + 2 + 5)^3 \\
 &:= (28 - 1 - 5 + 3 + 05 + 6 + 84 + 3)^5 & & &:= (2 - 82 - 33 + 3161 + 2 - 5)^3 \\
 &:= (-2 + 81 + 5 + 3 - 05 + 6 - 8 + 43)^5 & & \mathbf{28456429877} := (2 + 8 + 4 - 5 + 64 + 2987 - 7)^3 \\
 &:= (-2 + 81 - 5 + 3 + 05 + 6 - 8 + 43)^5 & & &:= (2 - 8 - 4 + 5 + 64 + 2987 + 7)^3 \\
 &:= (-2 + 81 - 5 - 3 - 05 + 6 + 8 + 43)^5 & & \mathbf{28534304241} := (-2 - 8 + 5 - 3 + 430 - 4 - 2 - 4 - 1)^4 \\
 &:= (-2 - 8 + 153 - 05 - 6 - 8 - 4 + 3)^5 & & &:= (2 - 8 - 5 + 3 + 430 - 4 - 2 - 4 - 1)^4 \\
 &:= (-2 + 8 - 1 + 53 + 056 + 8 + 4 - 3)^5 & & &:= (-2 - 8 - 5 + 3 + 430 - 4 + 2 - 4 - 1)^4 \\
 &:= (-2 + 8 + 1 + 53 + 056 + 8 - 4 + 3)^5 & & &:= (-2 - 8 - 5 - 3 + 430 + 4 - 2 - 4 + 1)^4 \\
 &:= (2 + 8 - 1 + 5 + 3 - 05 + 68 + 43)^5 & & &:= (2 - 8 - 5 - 3 + 430 - 4 + 2 - 4 + 1)^4 \\
 &:= (-2 + 8 - 1 + 5 - 3 + 05 + 68 + 43)^5 & & &:= (-2 - 8 - 5 - 3 + 430 - 4 - 2 + 4 + 1)^4 \\
 &:= (2 + 8 - 1 - 5 + 3 + 05 + 68 + 43)^5 & & &:= (-28 + 5 + 3 + 430 + 4 + 2 - 4 - 1)^4 \\
 &:= (-28 + 153 - 05 - 6 + 8 + 4 - 3)^5 & & &:= (-28 + 5 + 3 + 430 - 4 + 2 + 4 - 1)^4 \\
 &:= (-28 + 153 + 05 - 6 - 8 + 4 + 3)^5 & & &:= (-28 - 5 + 3 + 430 + 4 + 2 + 4 + 1)^4 \\
 &:= (28 + 1 + 53 + 056 - 8 - 4 - 3)^5 & & &:= (2 + 8 + 5 + 3 + 430 - 42 + 4 + 1)^4 \\
 &:= (28 - 1 - 5 + 30 + 56 + 8 + 4 + 3)^5 & & &:= (2 + 8 - 5 - 3 + 430 + 4 - 24 - 1)^4 \\
 &:= (2 + 81 + 5 - 30 + 56 + 8 + 4 - 3)^5 & & &:= (2 - 8 + 5 + 3 + 430 + 4 - 24 - 1)^4 \\
 &:= (2 + 8 + 153 + 05 + 6 - 8 - 43)^5 & & &:= (-2 + 8 + 5 - 3 + 430 - 4 - 24 + 1)^4 \\
 &:= (-2 + 8 + 153 + 05 - 6 + 8 - 43)^5 & & &:= (2 + 8 - 5 + 3 + 430 - 4 - 24 + 1)^4 \\
 &:= (2 - 8 + 153 + 05 + 6 + 8 - 43)^5 & & &:= (-2 + 8 + 5 + 3 + 4 - 30 + 424 - 1)^4 \\
 &:= (-2 + 8 + 15 + 30 + 5 + 68 - 4 + 3)^5 & & &:= (2 + 8 + 5 - 3 + 4 - 30 + 424 + 1)^4 \\
 &:= (-2 - 8 + 15 + 30 - 5 + 6 + 84 + 3)^5 & & &:= (28 - 5 + 343 + 042 + 4 - 1)^4
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 & := (28 + 5 + 343 - 04 - 2 + 41)^4 \\
 & := (28 - 5 - 34 - 3 + 0424 + 1)^4 \\
 & := (28 - 5 - 3 + 430 - 42 + 4 - 1)^4 \\
 & := (28 - 5 + 3 + 430 - 42 - 4 + 1)^4 \\
 & := (28 - 5 - 3 + 430 + 4 - 2 - 41)^4 \\
 & := (28 - 5 - 3 - 4 - 30 + 424 + 1)^4 \\
 & := (2 + 85 + 343 + 04 - 24 + 1)^4 \\
 & := (-2 + 85 - 3 + 4 + 304 + 24 - 1)^4 \\
 & := (-2 + 85 + 3 - 4 + 304 + 24 + 1)^4 \\
 & := (-2 - 8 - 5 + 343 + 042 + 41)^4 \\
 & := (-2 - 8 - 5 - 3 + 430 - 42 + 41)^4 \\
 & := (-28 + 5 + 3 + 430 + 42 - 41)^4 \\
 & := (-2 - 8 + 534 - 30 - 42 - 41)^4 \\
 \mathbf{28568426193} & := (2856 + 8 + 4 + 2 - 6 + 193)^3 \\
 & := (2856 + 8 - 4 - 2 + 6 + 193)^3 \\
 \mathbf{28793299625} & := (2 - 8 + 79 + 3 + 2996 - 2 - 5)^3 \\
 & := (-2 - 8 + 79 + 3 + 2996 + 2 - 5)^3 \\
 & := (-2 - 8 + 79 - 3 + 2996 - 2 + 5)^3 \\
 & := (-2 - 8 - 7 + 93 + 2996 - 2 - 5)^3 \\
 & := (-28 + 7 + 93 + 2996 + 2 - 5)^3 \\
 & := (2 - 8 + 7 + 93 + 2996 - 25)^3 \\
 \mathbf{28813025536} & := (2 + 88 + 1 + 302 + 5 + 5 + 3 + 6)^4 \\
 & := (2 + 8 + 81 + 302 + 5 + 5 + 3 + 6)^4 \\
 & := (28 + 81 + 302 + 5 + 5 - 3 - 6)^4 \\
 & := (2 - 88 - 1 - 30 - 2 - 5 + 536)^4 \\
 & := (-2 - 88 - 1 - 30 + 2 - 5 + 536)^4 \\
 & := (2 - 8 - 81 - 30 - 2 - 5 + 536)^4 \\
 & := (-2 - 8 - 81 - 30 + 2 - 5 + 536)^4 \\
 & := (2 + 8 + 8 + 130 + 255 + 3 + 6)^4 \\
 & := (2 + 8 + 8 + 1 + 302 + 55 + 36)^4 \\
 & := (288 + 1 + 30 + 2 + 55 + 36)^4 \\
 & := (28 + 8 + 130 + 255 - 3 - 6)^4 \\
 & := (28 - 8 - 1 + 302 + 55 + 36)^4 \\
 & := (2 - 88 - 13 - 025 + 536)^4 \\
 & := (2 + 88 + 1 + 302 + 55 - 36)^4 \\
 & := (2 + 88 + 1 + 30 + 255 + 36)^4 \\
 & := (2 + 8 + 81 + 302 + 55 - 36)^4 \\
 & := (2 + 8 + 81 + 30 + 255 + 36)^4 \\
 & := (288 + 130 + 25 + 5 - 36)^4 \\
 \mathbf{28877930432} & := (2 + 8 + 8 + 7 - 7 + 9 + 3043 - 2)^3 \\
 & := (2 + 8 + 8 - 7 + 7 + 9 + 3043 - 2)^3 \\
 & := (2 + 8 + 8 + 7 + 7 - 9 + 3043 + 2)^3 \\
 & := (-2 + 8 + 8 + 7 - 7 + 9 + 3043 + 2)^3 \\
 & := (-2 + 8 + 8 - 7 + 7 + 9 + 3043 + 2)^3 \\
 & := (28 + 8 + 7 - 7 - 9 + 3043 - 2)^3 \\
 & := (28 + 8 - 7 + 7 - 9 + 3043 - 2)^3 \\
 \mathbf{28906177509} & := (2890 + 6 + 177 + 5 - 09)^3 \\
 & := (2890 + 61 + 77 + 50 - 9)^3 \\
 \mathbf{28934443000} & := (2 + 8 + 9 + 3 + 44 + 4 + 3000)^3 \\
 & := (2 + 8 + 9 + 3 + 4 + 44 + 3000)^3 \\
 & := (28 - 9 + 3 + 44 + 4 + 3000)^3 \\
 & := (28 - 9 + 3 + 4 + 44 + 3000)^3 \\
 \mathbf{28958169241} & := (-28 + 958 + 169241)^2 \\
 \mathbf{29047689224} & := (2904 + 76 + 8 + 92 - 2 - 4)^3 \\
 \mathbf{29093783761} & := (2 + 9 + 09 + 378 + 3 + 7 + 6 - 1)^4 \\
 & := (2 + 9 + 09 + 3 + 7 + 8 + 376 - 1)^4 \\
 & := (290 + 93 + 7 + 8 + 3 + 7 + 6 - 1)^4 \\
 & := (29 + 09 + 378 - 3 + 7 - 6 - 1)^4 \\
 & := (29 - 09 + 378 + 3 + 7 + 6 - 1)^4 \\
 & := (29 + 09 + 378 - 3 - 7 + 6 + 1)^4 \\
 & := (29 - 09 + 3 + 7 + 8 + 376 - 1)^4 \\
 & := (29 + 09 - 3 - 7 + 8 + 376 + 1)^4 \\
 & := (2 - 9 - 09 + 378 - 3 - 7 + 61)^4 \\
 & := (290 - 9 + 37 + 83 + 7 + 6 - 1)^4 \\
 & := (290 - 9 + 3 + 78 - 3 - 7 + 61)^4 \\
 & := (290 - 9 - 3 + 78 + 3 - 7 + 61)^4 \\
 & := (-2 + 90 - 9 + 378 - 37 - 6 - 1)^4 \\
 & := (2 + 90 - 9 - 37 - 8 + 376 - 1)^4 \\
 & := (290 + 9 - 37 + 83 + 7 + 61)^4 \\
 & := (-290 - 9 - 3 + 783 - 7 - 61)^4 \\
 \mathbf{29132817533} & := (2913 + 2 + 81 + 75 + 3 + 3)^3 \\
 & := (291 - 3 + 2817 + 5 - 33)^3 \\
 & := (2 - 9 + 1328 + 1753 + 3)^3 \\
 \mathbf{29161230552} & := (2 + 9 + 1 + 6 + 1 + 2 + 3055 + 2)^3 \\
 & := (29 + 1 - 6 - 1 + 2 + 3055 - 2)^3 \\
 & := (29 - 1 - 6 + 1 + 2 + 3055 - 2)^3
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 &:= (29 + 1 - 6 - 1 - 2 + 3055 + 2)^3 & &:= (293 + 7 + 6 + 5 + 8 + 88 + 1 + 6)^4 \\
 &:= (29 - 1 - 6 + 1 - 2 + 3055 + 2)^3 & &:= (293 + 7 + 6 + 5 + 8 + 8 + 81 + 6)^4 \\
 &:= (2 - 9 + 16 + 12 + 3055 + 2)^3 & &:= (-2 - 9 + 376 + 58 - 8 - 8 + 1 + 6)^4 \\
 &:= (29 - 16 + 12 + 3055 - 2)^3 & &:= (2 - 9 + 376 + 5 + 8 + 8 + 8 + 16)^4 \\
 \mathbf{29189662039} &:= (2918 + 96 + 6 + 20 + 39)^3 & &:= (293 + 76 + 5 + 8 + 8 + 8 + 16)^4 \\
 \mathbf{29281712161} &:= (2 - 92 - 8 + 171216 + 1)^2 & &:= (-29 + 376 + 58 + 8 + 8 - 1 - 6)^4 \\
 \mathbf{29303572787} &:= (29 + 3035 + 7 + 27 - 8 - 7)^3 & &:= (-2 - 93 - 76 + 588 - 8 - 1 + 6)^4 \\
 &:= (29 + 3035 - 7 + 27 - 8 + 7)^3 & &:= (29 + 376 - 58 - 8 + 81 - 6)^4 \\
 \mathbf{29316250624} &:= (2 + 93 - 1 - 6 - 2 + 50 - 6 - 2 - 4)^5 & &\mathbf{29389200056} := (2938 + 92 + 00056)^3 \\
 &:= (-2 + 93 - 1 - 6 + 2 + 50 - 6 - 2 - 4)^5 & &\mathbf{29417779503} := (2941 + 77 + 7 + 9 + 50 + 3)^3 \\
 &:= (-2 + 93 - 1 - 6 - 2 + 50 - 6 + 2 - 4)^5 & &:= (2941 + 7 + 77 + 9 + 50 + 3)^3 \\
 &:= (-2 + 9 + 3 - 1 + 62 - 5 + 062 - 4)^5 & &:= (2941 + 7 + 7 + 79 + 50 + 3)^3 \\
 &:= (2 + 9 - 3 + 1 + 62 - 5 + 062 - 4)^5 & &\mathbf{29446377472} := (2944 - 6 - 3 + 77 + 4 + 72)^3 \\
 &:= (-2 - 9 + 3 - 1 + 62 + 5 + 062 + 4)^5 & &:= (2944 - 6 - 3 + 7 + 74 + 72)^3 \\
 &:= (2 - 9 - 3 + 1 + 62 + 5 + 062 + 4)^5 & &\mathbf{29474993969} := (2947 + 49 + 9 - 3 + 96 - 9)^3 \\
 &:= (29 - 3 + 1 + 62 + 5 + 06 + 24)^5 & &:= (2947 + 49 - 9 - 3 + 96 + 9)^3 \\
 &:= (29 - 3 + 1 + 6 + 25 + 062 + 4)^5 & &\mathbf{29532282571} := (2953 + 2 - 2 + 82 + 57 - 1)^3 \\
 &:= (2 + 93 + 16 + 25 - 06 - 2 - 4)^5 & &:= (2953 - 2 + 2 + 82 + 57 - 1)^3 \\
 &:= (-2 + 93 + 16 + 25 - 06 + 2 - 4)^5 & &:= (295 - 3 + 228 + 2571)^3 \\
 &:= (2 + 93 + 1 + 6 + 2 + 50 - 6 - 24)^5 & &\mathbf{29647082375} := (2964 + 7 + 082 + 37 + 5)^3 \\
 &:= (2 + 93 + 1 - 6 + 2 + 50 + 6 - 24)^5 & &\mathbf{29661450625} := (-2 - 9 - 6 - 6 + 1 + 450 - 6 - 2 - 5)^4 \\
 &:= (2 - 9 + 31 + 62 + 50 - 6 - 2 - 4)^5 & &:= (2 + 9 + 6 - 61 + 450 + 6 - 2 + 5)^4 \\
 &:= (-2 - 9 + 31 + 62 + 50 - 6 + 2 - 4)^5 & &:= (-2 + 9 + 6 - 61 + 450 + 6 + 2 + 5)^4 \\
 &:= (2 - 9 + 31 - 6 - 2 + 50 + 62 - 4)^5 & &:= (2 + 9 + 6 + 6 - 1 + 450 - 62 + 5)^4 \\
 &:= (-2 - 9 + 31 - 6 + 2 + 50 + 62 - 4)^5 & &:= (-2 + 9 - 6 - 6 + 1 + 450 - 6 - 25)^4 \\
 &:= (2 + 9 - 3 + 162 - 50 + 6 + 2 - 4)^5 & &:= (296 + 61 + 45 + 06 + 2 + 5)^4 \\
 &:= (-2 + 9 - 3 + 162 - 50 + 6 - 2 + 4)^5 & &:= (296 + 61 - 4 + 5 + 062 - 5)^4 \\
 &:= (2 - 9 - 3 + 16 + 2 + 50 + 62 + 4)^5 & &:= (296 + 61 - 4 - 5 + 062 + 5)^4 \\
 &:= (293 - 162 + 5 - 06 - 2 - 4)^5 & &:= (296 + 6 + 1 + 45 + 062 + 5)^4 \\
 &:= (29 + 31 - 6 + 2 + 50 - 6 + 24)^5 & &:= (29 - 66 - 1 + 450 + 6 + 2 - 5)^4 \\
 &:= (29 - 3 - 16 - 2 + 50 + 62 + 4)^5 & &:= (29 - 66 + 1 + 450 - 6 + 2 + 5)^4 \\
 &:= (29 - 3 + 16 + 2 + 50 + 6 + 24)^5 & &:= (-29 - 66 + 1 - 4 + 506 + 2 + 5)^4 \\
 &:= (2 - 93 + 162 - 5 + 062 - 4)^5 & &:= (29 + 6 - 61 + 450 - 6 + 2 - 5)^4 \\
 &:= (2 + 93 - 1 + 62 - 50 - 6 + 24)^5 & &:= (29 - 6 - 61 + 450 + 6 + 2 - 5)^4 \\
 &:= (2 - 93 + 1 - 6 + 250 - 6 - 24)^5 & &:= (-29 + 6 - 61 - 4 + 506 + 2 - 5)^4 \\
 &:= (2 + 9 + 31 + 62 + 50 - 6 - 24)^5 & &:= (-29 + 6 + 6 + 1 + 450 + 6 - 25)^4 \\
 &:= (293 + 1 - 62 - 50 - 62 + 4)^5 & &:= (2 + 9 - 66 + 1 + 450 - 6 + 25)^4 \\
 \mathbf{29376588816} &:= (293 + 7 + 6 + 5 + 88 + 8 + 1 + 6)^4 & &:= (-2 - 9 + 6 - 61 + 450 + 6 + 25)^4
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 &:= (2 - 9 + 6 - 61 - 4 + 506 - 25)^4 \\
 &:= (-2 - 966 + 1450 - 62 - 5)^4 \\
 \mathbf{29663172900} &:= (2 - 9 - 663 + 172900)^2 \\
 \mathbf{29675828736} &:= (2967 + 58 + 28 + 7 + 36)^3 \\
 &:= (296 - 75 + 8 + 2873 - 6)^3 \\
 \mathbf{29704593673} &:= (2970 + 45 + 9 + 3 + 67 + 3)^3 \\
 &:= (2970 + 4 + 59 - 3 - 6 + 73)^3 \\
 &:= (2970 + 4 + 5 + 9 + 36 + 73)^3 \\
 &:= (2970 - 45 + 93 + 6 + 73)^3 \\
 \mathbf{29733377192} &:= (-297 - 3 + 3377 + 19 + 2)^3 \\
 \mathbf{29869171929} &:= (29 + 869 + 171929)^2 \\
 \mathbf{29906468864} &:= (2990 + 6 + 4 + 6 + 88 + 6 + 4)^3 \\
 &:= (2990 + 6 + 4 + 6 + 8 + 86 + 4)^3 \\
 &:= (2990 + 64 + 68 - 8 - 6 - 4)^3 \\
 &:= (2990 - 6 + 46 - 8 + 86 - 4)^3 \\
 &:= (2990 - 6 - 4 + 68 - 8 + 64)^3 \\
 \mathbf{29935382625} &:= (2993 + 5 + 38 + 2 + 62 + 5)^3 \\
 &:= (2993 + 53 + 8 + 26 + 25)^3 \\
 \mathbf{29948379136} &:= (2 + 9 + 9 + 483 - 79 + 1 - 3 - 6)^4 \\
 &:= (-2 + 9 + 9 + 483 - 79 - 1 + 3 - 6)^4 \\
 &:= (2 + 9 - 9 + 483 - 79 + 1 + 3 + 6)^4 \\
 &:= (2 - 9 + 9 + 483 - 79 + 1 + 3 + 6)^4 \\
 &:= (2 + 9 + 9 + 483 + 7 - 91 + 3 - 6)^4 \\
 &:= (2 - 9 - 9 + 483 - 7 - 9 + 1 - 36)^4 \\
 &:= (-2 + 9 - 9 - 4 + 8 + 379 - 1 + 36)^4 \\
 &:= (-2 - 9 + 9 - 4 + 8 + 379 - 1 + 36)^4 \\
 &:= (299 - 4 + 8 - 3 + 79 + 1 + 36)^4 \\
 &:= (29 - 9 + 483 - 79 + 1 - 3 - 6)^4 \\
 &:= (29 - 9 + 483 + 7 - 91 + 3 - 6)^4 \\
 &:= (299 + 48 - 3 + 79 - 13 + 6)^4 \\
 &:= (-299 + 4 - 83 + 791 - 3 + 6)^4 \\
 \mathbf{29964315016} &:= (-29 - 9 + 6 + 4 + 3150 - 16)^3 \\
 &:= (-2 - 99 + 64 + 3150 - 1 - 6)^3 \\
 \mathbf{29964315016} &:= (2996 + 43 + 1 + 50 + 16)^3 \\
 \mathbf{29993266043} &:= (2999 - 3 + 2 + 66 + 043)^3 \\
 &:= (2999 - 3 + 2 + 6 + 60 + 43)^3 \\
 \mathbf{30109256631} &:= (3010 + 92 - 5 + 6 + 6 + 3 - 1)^3 \\
 &:= (3010 + 92 + 5 + 6 - 6 + 3 + 1)^3
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 &:= (3010 + 92 + 5 - 6 + 6 + 3 + 1)^3 \\
 \mathbf{30167363897} &:= (3016 + 7 + 3 + 63 + 8 + 9 + 7)^3 \\
 &:= (3016 + 7 + 3 - 6 - 3 + 89 + 7)^3 \\
 &:= (3016 + 7 - 3 - 6 + 3 + 89 + 7)^3 \\
 &:= (3016 + 7 + 36 + 38 + 9 + 7)^3 \\
 \mathbf{30196445544} &:= (3019 + 6 + 44 - 5 + 54 - 4)^3 \\
 &:= (3019 + 644 - 5 - 544)^3 \\
 \mathbf{30225545875} &:= (3022 + 5 + 5 - 4 + 5 + 87 - 5)^3 \\
 &:= (3022 + 5 + 5 - 4 - 5 + 87 + 5)^3 \\
 &:= (3022 + 5 - 5 - 4 + 5 + 87 + 5)^3 \\
 &:= (3022 - 5 + 5 - 4 + 5 + 87 + 5)^3 \\
 &:= (3022 + 55 - 45 + 8 + 75)^3 \\
 &:= (30 + 2255 - 45 + 875)^3 \\
 \mathbf{30237384321} &:= (3 - 02 + 3 - 7 - 3 - 8 + 432 - 1)^4 \\
 &:= (3 - 02 - 3 - 7 + 3 - 8 + 432 - 1)^4 \\
 &:= (-3 - 02 + 3 - 7 + 3 - 8 + 432 - 1)^4 \\
 &:= (3 + 02 - 3 - 7 - 3 - 8 + 432 + 1)^4 \\
 &:= (-3 + 02 + 3 - 7 - 3 - 8 + 432 + 1)^4 \\
 &:= (-3 + 02 - 3 - 7 + 3 - 8 + 432 + 1)^4 \\
 &:= (30 + 2 + 373 + 8 + 4 + 3 - 2 - 1)^4 \\
 &:= (30 - 2 + 373 + 8 + 4 + 3 + 2 - 1)^4 \\
 &:= (30 + 2 + 373 + 8 + 4 - 3 + 2 + 1)^4 \\
 &:= (3 + 023 + 7 + 384 + 3 - 2 - 1)^4 \\
 &:= (3 + 023 + 7 + 384 - 3 + 2 + 1)^4 \\
 &:= (-3 + 023 + 7 + 384 + 3 + 2 + 1)^4 \\
 &:= (-3 - 023 + 7 - 3 + 8 + 432 - 1)^4 \\
 &:= (3 - 023 - 7 + 3 + 8 + 432 + 1)^4 \\
 &:= (3 - 02 + 373 + 8 + 4 + 32 - 1)^4 \\
 &:= (-3 + 02 + 373 + 8 + 4 + 32 + 1)^4 \\
 &:= (3 + 02 + 3 + 7 + 384 - 3 + 21)^4 \\
 &:= (3 + 02 - 3 + 7 + 384 + 3 + 21)^4 \\
 &:= (-3 + 02 + 3 + 7 + 384 + 3 + 21)^4 \\
 &:= (3 + 02 + 3 + 7 - 3 + 84 + 321)^4 \\
 &:= (3 + 02 - 3 + 7 + 3 + 84 + 321)^4 \\
 &:= (-3 + 02 + 3 + 7 + 3 + 84 + 321)^4 \\
 &:= (302 - 3 + 73 + 8 + 4 + 32 + 1)^4 \\
 &:= (302 + 3 + 7 + 3 + 84 - 3 + 21)^4 \\
 &:= (302 + 3 + 7 - 3 + 84 + 3 + 21)^4
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} &:= (302 - 3 + 7 + 3 + 84 + 3 + 21)^4 \\ &:= (30 + 2 + 373 - 8 - 4 + 3 + 21)^4 \\ &:= (30 - 2 - 37 + 3 - 8 + 432 - 1)^4 \\ &:= (30 + 2 - 37 - 3 - 8 + 432 + 1)^4 \\ &:= (30 + 2 + 3 + 73 - 8 - 4 + 321)^4 \\ &:= (30 - 2 + 3 - 7 - 38 + 432 - 1)^4 \\ &:= (30 + 2 - 3 - 7 - 38 + 432 + 1)^4 \\ &:= (3 - 02 + 3 + 738 - 4 - 321)^4 \\ &:= (-3 + 02 - 3 + 738 + 4 - 321)^4 \\ &:= (302 + 37 + 38 + 43 - 2 - 1)^4 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} &:= (-302 + 3 + 738 - 4 + 3 - 21)^4 \\ &:= (30 - 23 - 7 + 384 + 32 + 1)^4 \\ &:= (-30 + 23 + 7 + 384 + 32 + 1)^4 \\ &:= (-30 + 2 + 373 + 8 + 43 + 21)^4 \\ &:= (-30 + 2 + 37 + 384 + 3 + 21)^4 \\ &:= (-30 + 2 + 37 + 3 + 84 + 321)^4 \\ &:= (-302 + 3 + 738 - 43 + 21)^4 \\ &:= (-30 - 2 - 373 + 843 - 21)^4 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{30254664896} &:= (3025 + 4 + 6 - 6 + 4 + 89 - 6)^3 \\ &:= (3025 + 4 - 6 + 6 + 4 + 89 - 6)^3 \\ &:= (3025 + 4 - 6 - 6 + 4 + 89 + 6)^3 \\ &:= (3025 + 46 - 6 + 48 + 9 - 6)^3 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} &:= (30 + 5 + 1 - 7 - 5 - 7 - 8 - 1 + 2 - 5)^{15} \\ &:= (30 - 5 + 1 - 7 + 5 - 7 - 8 - 1 + 2 - 5)^{15} \\ &:= (30 + 5 - 1 - 7 - 5 - 7 - 8 + 1 + 2 - 5)^{15} \\ &:= (30 - 5 - 1 - 7 + 5 - 7 - 8 + 1 + 2 - 5)^{15} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{30283802613} &:= (3028 + 3 + 80 + 2 + 6 + 1 - 3)^3 \\ &:= (3028 + 3 + 80 - 2 + 6 - 1 + 3)^3 \\ &:= (3028 - 3 + 80 + 2 + 6 + 1 + 3)^3 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} &:= (-30 + 5 + 1 + 7 + 5 + 7 + 8 - 1 - 2 + 5)^{15} \\ &:= (-30 + 5 - 1 + 7 + 5 + 7 + 8 + 1 - 2 + 5)^{15} \\ &:= (30 - 5 + 1 - 7 - 5 - 7 - 8 - 1 + 2 + 5)^{15} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{30312959032} &:= (3031 + 2 + 95 - 9 - 03 + 2)^3 \\ &:= (3031 - 2 + 9 - 5 + 90 - 3 - 2)^3 \\ &:= (3031 + 2 - 9 + 5 + 90 - 3 + 2)^3 \\ &:= (-30 + 3129 + 5 + 9 + 03 + 2)^3 \\ &:= (3031 + 29 + 59 - 03 + 2)^3 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} &:= (30 - 5 - 1 - 7 - 5 - 7 - 8 + 1 + 2 + 5)^{15} \\ &:= (-3 + 05 + 17 - 5 + 7 - 8 - 1 - 2 - 5)^{15} \\ &:= (-3 - 05 + 17 + 5 + 7 - 8 - 1 - 2 - 5)^{15} \\ &:= (3 - 05 + 17 - 5 - 7 + 8 + 1 - 2 - 5)^{15} \\ &:= (3 + 05 - 17 + 5 + 7 + 8 + 1 - 2 - 5)^{15} \end{aligned}$$

$$\mathbf{30342134159} := (3034 - 2 - 13 + 41 + 59)^3$$

$$:= (-3 + 05 + 17 + 5 - 7 - 8 - 1 + 2 - 5)^{15}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{30429771848} &:= (3042 - 9 + 7 + 7 - 1 + 84 - 8)^3 \\ &:= (3042 + 9 + 7 + 7 + 1 + 8 + 48)^3 \\ &:= (3042 + 9 + 77 - 18 + 4 + 8)^3 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} &:= (3 - 05 + 17 - 5 + 7 - 8 - 1 + 2 - 5)^{15} \\ &:= (-3 - 05 + 17 - 5 + 7 - 8 - 1 - 2 + 5)^{15} \\ &:= (3 + 05 - 17 - 5 + 7 + 8 + 1 - 2 + 5)^{15} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{30459021867} &:= (3045 + 90 - 2 - 1 - 8 + 6 - 7)^3 \\ &:= (3045 + 90 - 21 + 8 - 6 + 7)^3 \\ &:= (3045 - 9 + 02 + 18 + 67)^3 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} &:= (3 - 05 - 17 + 5 + 7 + 8 + 1 - 2 + 5)^{15} \\ &:= (-3 + 05 + 17 - 5 - 7 - 8 - 1 + 2 + 5)^{15} \\ &:= (-3 - 05 + 17 + 5 - 7 - 8 - 1 + 2 + 5)^{15} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{30488290624} &:= (3048 - 8 + 2 + 90 - 6 + 2 - 4)^3 \\ &:= (3048 - 8 - 2 + 90 - 6 - 2 + 4)^3 \\ &:= (304 - 88 + 2906 - 2 + 4)^3 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} &:= (3 + 05 - 17 + 5 - 7 + 8 + 1 + 2 + 5)^{15} \\ &:= (3 + 05 + 1 + 7 + 5 - 7 + 8 - 12 - 5)^{15} \\ &:= (3 + 05 + 1 - 7 + 5 + 7 + 8 - 12 - 5)^{15} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{30517578125} &:= (30 - 5 + 1 + 7 - 5 - 7 - 8 - 1 - 2 - 5)^{15} \\ &:= (30 - 5 + 1 - 7 - 5 + 7 - 8 - 1 - 2 - 5)^{15} \\ &:= (30 - 5 - 1 - 7 - 5 - 7 + 8 - 1 - 2 - 5)^{15} \\ &:= (30 - 5 - 1 + 7 - 5 - 7 - 8 + 1 - 2 - 5)^{15} \\ &:= (30 - 5 - 1 - 7 - 5 + 7 - 8 + 1 - 2 - 5)^{15} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} &:= (-3 + 05 - 1 + 7 + 5 - 7 - 8 + 12 - 5)^{15} \\ &:= (3 - 05 - 1 + 7 - 5 + 7 - 8 + 12 - 5)^{15} \\ &:= (-3 + 05 - 1 - 7 + 5 + 7 - 8 + 12 - 5)^{15} \\ &:= (3 + 05 + 1 - 7 - 5 - 7 + 8 + 12 - 5)^{15} \\ &:= (3 - 05 + 1 - 7 + 5 - 7 + 8 + 12 - 5)^{15} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} & := (-3+05-1+7+5+7-8-12+5)^{15} & := (-3+05+1-75-7+81-2+5)^{15} \\ & := (3+05+1+7-5-7+8-12+5)^{15} & := (3-05-1+75+7-81+2+5)^{15} \\ & := (3-05+1+7+5-7+8-12+5)^{15} & := (3-05+1-75-7+81+2+5)^{15} \\ & := (3+05+1-7-5+7+8-12+5)^{15} & := (3+05+1+75+7+8+1+25)^5 \\ & := (3-05+1-7+5+7+8-12+5)^{15} & := (-3+05-1-7+57+81-2-5)^5 \\ & := (-3+05-1+7-5-7-8+12+5)^{15} & := (-3-05-1-7-57+81+2-5)^{15} \\ & := (-3-05-1+7+5-7-8+12+5)^{15} & := (3-05-1-7+57+81+2-5)^5 \\ & := (-3+05-1-7-5+7-8+12+5)^{15} & := (-3-05-1-7+57+81-2+5)^5 \\ & := (-3-05-1-7+5+7-8+12+5)^{15} & := (3+05+1+7+5+78+1+25)^5 \\ & := (3-05+1-7-5-7+8+12+5)^{15} & := (-3+05+1+7+5-7-8+125)^5 \\ & := (30+5+1+7+5-7+81-2+5)^5 & := (3-05+1+7-5+7-8+125)^5 \\ & := (30+5+1-7+5+7+81-2+5)^5 & := (-3+05+1-7+5+7-8+125)^5 \\ & := (30+5-1+7+5-7-8-1-25)^{15} & := (3-05-1+7-5-7+8+125)^5 \\ & := (30+5-1-7+5+7-8-1-25)^{15} & := (-3+05-1-7+5-7+8+125)^5 \\ & := (30-5+1+7-5-7+8+1-25)^{15} & := (3-05-1-7-5+7+8+125)^5 \\ & := (30-5+1-7-5+7+8+1-25)^{15} & := (-30-51+75+7+8-1+2-5)^{15} \\ & := (-30-5-1+7-5+7+8-1+25)^{15} & := (30+51-75-7+8+1+2-5)^{15} \\ & := (-30+5+1+7-5-7+8+1+25)^{15} & := (30+51-7-57-8-1+2-5)^{15} \\ & := (-30-5+1+7+5-7+8+1+25)^{15} & := (30+51-7+57-8-1-2+5)^5 \\ & := (-30+5+1-7-5+7+8+1+25)^{15} & := (-30-51+7+5+78-1+2-5)^{15} \\ & := (-30-5+1-7+5+7+8+1+25)^{15} & := (30+51-7+5-78+1-2+5)^{15} \\ & := (-3-051-7-5-7+81+2-5)^{15} & := (-30-51+7-5+78-1+2+5)^{15} \\ & := (-3+051-7+5-7-8-1-25)^{15} & := (-30+51+7-5+7-8-12-5)^{15} \\ & := (3-051+7+5+7+8+1+25)^{15} & := (30+51+7+5+7+8+12+5)^5 \\ & := (3+05+17+5+7+81+2+5)^5 & := (-30-5-17+57+8-1-2-5)^{15} \\ & := (3+05+17+5-7+8-1-25)^{15} & := (-30+5-17+57-8+1+2-5)^{15} \\ & := (3+05+17+5+7-8+1-25)^{15} & := (30+5+17-57+8-1-2+5)^{15} \\ & := (-3+05+17-5+7+8+1-25)^{15} & := (-30-5-17+57-8+1+2+5)^{15} \\ & := (-3-05+17+5+7+8+1-25)^{15} & := (30+5+17+57+8+1+2+5)^5 \\ & := (3+05-17+5-7-8-1+25)^{15} & := (30-5+17-5-7-8-12-5)^{15} \\ & := (-3+05-17-5-7+8-1+25)^{15} & := (30+5-17+5+7-8-12-5)^{15} \\ & := (-3-05-17+5-7+8-1+25)^{15} & := (30+5-17-5-7-8+12-5)^{15} \\ & := (-3+05-17-5+7-8+1+25)^{15} & := (30-5-17+5-7-8+12-5)^{15} \\ & := (-3-05-17+5+7-8+1+25)^{15} & := (-30+5+17+5-7+8+12-5)^{15} \\ & := (3-05+1-75+7+81-2-5)^{15} & := (30+5-17-5+7-8-12+5)^{15} \\ & := (3+05-1+75+7-81+2-5)^{15} & := (30-5-17+5+7-8-12+5)^{15} \\ & := (3+05+1-75-7+81+2-5)^{15} & := (-30+5+17+5+7+8-12+5)^{15} \\ & := (-3+05-1+75+7-81-2+5)^{15} & := (30-5-17-5-7-8+12+5)^{15} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 & := (-30 + 5 + 17 - 5 - 7 + 8 + 12 + 5)^{15} & := (30 - 51 + 75 - 7 + 81 + 2 - 5)^5 \\
 & := (-30 - 5 + 17 + 5 - 7 + 8 + 12 + 5)^{15} & := (-30 - 51 + 75 - 7 - 8 + 1 + 25)^{15} \\
 & := (-30 + 5 + 1 + 75 + 78 - 1 + 2 - 5)^5 & := (-30 + 51 + 7 - 57 + 8 + 1 + 25)^{15} \\
 & := (-30 + 5 - 1 + 75 + 78 + 1 + 2 - 5)^5 & := (-30 + 51 + 7 - 5 + 78 - 1 + 25)^5 \\
 & := (-30 - 5 + 1 + 75 + 78 - 1 + 2 + 5)^5 & := (30 + 5 + 175 - 7 - 81 - 2 + 5)^5 \\
 & := (-30 - 5 - 1 + 75 + 78 + 1 + 2 + 5)^5 & := (-30 + 5 + 175 - 7 + 8 - 1 - 25)^5 \\
 & := (30 + 5 - 1 + 75 + 7 - 8 + 12 + 5)^5 & := (-30 + 5 + 175 + 7 - 8 + 1 - 25)^5 \\
 & := (-30 - 5 + 1 + 7 + 57 - 8 - 12 - 5)^{15} & := (-30 - 5 + 17 + 57 - 8 - 1 - 25)^{15} \\
 & := (-30 - 5 - 1 - 7 + 57 + 8 - 12 - 5)^{15} & := (30 + 5 + 17 + 57 - 8 - 1 + 25)^5 \\
 & := (30 + 5 + 1 + 7 + 57 + 8 + 12 + 5)^5 & := (-30 + 5 - 17 - 5 + 78 - 1 - 25)^{15} \\
 & := (30 - 5 - 1 + 7 - 5 - 7 + 81 + 25)^5 & := (-30 - 5 - 17 + 5 + 78 - 1 - 25)^{15} \\
 & := (30 - 5 - 1 - 7 - 5 + 7 + 81 + 25)^5 & := (30 + 5 - 17 + 5 + 78 - 1 + 25)^5 \\
 & := (-3 - 051 + 75 - 7 + 8 - 12 - 5)^{15} & := (30 + 5 + 17 + 5 - 78 + 1 + 25)^{15} \\
 & := (3 - 051 + 75 - 7 - 8 - 12 + 5)^{15} & := (30 + 5 - 1 + 75 - 78 - 1 - 25)^{15} \\
 & := (-3 + 051 + 75 - 7 - 8 + 12 + 5)^5 & := (30 - 5 + 1 - 75 + 78 + 1 - 25)^{15} \\
 & := (-3 + 051 - 75 + 7 + 8 + 12 + 5)^{15} & := (-30 + 5 + 1 - 75 + 78 + 1 + 25)^{15} \\
 & := (3 + 051 - 7 - 57 + 8 + 12 - 5)^{15} & := (-3 - 051 + 75 + 78 + 1 + 25)^5 \\
 & := (3 + 051 + 7 - 57 + 8 - 12 + 5)^{15} & := (3 + 051 + 75 - 7 + 8 - 125)^{15} \\
 & := (-3 - 051 - 7 + 57 - 8 + 12 + 5)^{15} & := (3 - 051 - 7 - 57 - 8 + 125)^{15} \\
 & := (-3 - 051 - 7 + 5 + 78 - 12 - 5)^{15} & := (3 + 051 - 7 + 5 + 78 - 125)^{15} \\
 & := (-3 - 051 - 7 - 5 + 78 - 12 + 5)^{15} & := (-3 - 051 + 7 + 5 - 78 + 125)^{15} \\
 & := (3 + 051 + 7 + 5 - 78 + 12 + 5)^{15} & := (-3 + 05 + 175 - 78 + 1 + 25)^5 \\
 & := (3 + 05 + 17 + 5 + 78 + 12 + 5)^5 & := (-3 + 05 + 1 + 75 - 78 + 125)^5 \\
 & := (-3 + 05 - 1 + 75 - 78 + 12 - 5)^{15} & := (3 - 05 - 1 - 75 + 78 + 125)^5 \\
 & := (3 + 05 + 1 - 75 + 78 - 12 + 5)^{15} & := (305 - 1 - 75 - 78 - 1 - 25)^5 \\
 & := (-3 - 05 - 1 + 75 - 78 + 12 + 5)^{15} & := (305 + 1 - 7 - 57 + 8 - 125)^5 \\
 & := (-3 + 05 - 1 + 75 - 7 + 81 - 25)^5 & := (30 - 51 + 75 + 78 - 12 + 5)^5 \\
 & := (-3 - 05 + 1 + 75 - 7 - 81 + 25)^{15} & := (30 - 51 + 75 + 7 - 81 + 25)^{15} \\
 & := (3 - 05 + 1 + 7 - 57 + 81 - 25)^{15} & := (30 + 5 + 175 - 78 - 12 + 5)^5 \\
 & := (3 - 05 - 1 + 7 + 57 - 81 + 25)^{15} & := (305 - 17 - 57 - 81 - 25)^5 \\
 & := (3051 + 75 - 7 + 8 + 1 + 2 - 5)^3 & := (-30 - 517 + 578 - 1 - 25)^{15} \\
 & := (3051 + 7 + 57 + 8 - 1 - 2 + 5)^3 & \mathbf{30528476176} := (305 + 2 + 84 + 7 + 6 + 1 + 7 + 6)^4 \\
 & := (3051 + 7 - 5 + 78 + 1 - 2 - 5)^3 & := (305 + 28 + 4 + 7 + 61 + 7 + 6)^4 \\
 & := (3051 - 7 + 5 + 78 + 1 + 2 - 5)^3 & := (305 - 2 + 8 + 47 + 61 - 7 + 6)^4 \\
 & := (3051 - 7 - 5 + 78 + 1 + 2 + 5)^3 & := (305 + 2 + 8 + 4 + 76 + 17 + 6)^4 \\
 & := (305 - 175 - 7 + 8 + 1 - 2 - 5)^5 & := (-30 + 528 - 4 - 76 - 1 + 7 - 6)^4 \\
 & := (305 - 175 + 7 - 8 - 1 + 2 - 5)^5 & := (-30 + 528 - 4 - 76 + 1 - 7 + 6)^4 \\
 & := (-30 + 51 + 75 - 7 - 81 + 2 - 5)^{15} & := (-30 + 528 - 4 + 7 - 6 - 1 - 76)^4
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 & := (-30 + 528 - 4 - 7 + 6 + 1 - 76)^4 \\
 & := (-30 + 5 - 2 - 8 + 476 - 17 - 6)^4 \\
 & := (30 - 5 + 2 - 8 + 476 - 1 - 76)^4 \\
 & := (-3 + 0528 - 47 - 61 + 7 - 6)^4 \\
 & := (-3 - 052 + 8 + 476 - 17 + 6)^4 \\
 & := (305 - 2 - 8 - 47 - 6 + 176)^4 \\
 & := (30 + 528 + 4 - 7 - 61 - 76)^4 \\
 & := (30 + 5 + 284 + 76 + 17 + 6)^4 \\
 & := (30 + 52 + 84 + 76 + 176)^4 \\
 \mathbf{30546884376} & := (3054 + 68 - 8 - 4 + 3 + 7 + 6)^3 \\
 & := (3054 + 6 - 8 + 84 + 3 - 7 - 6)^3 \\
 & := (3054 - 6 - 8 + 84 + 3 - 7 + 6)^3 \\
 \mathbf{30576209383} & := (3057 + 6 + 20 + 9 + 38 - 3)^3 \\
 \mathbf{30605553152} & := (-3 - 06 - 05 - 5 - 5 + 3152)^3 \\
 & := (3060 - 5 - 5 - 5 + 31 + 52)^3 \\
 & := (30 + 6 - 055 - 5 + 3152)^3 \\
 & := (30 + 6 - 05 - 55 + 3152)^3 \\
 \mathbf{30634915689} & := (3063 + 49 + 1 + 5 - 6 + 8 + 9)^3 \\
 & := (3063 + 49 - 1 - 5 + 6 + 8 + 9)^3 \\
 & := (3063 + 4 + 9 - 1 - 5 + 68 - 9)^3 \\
 & := (3063 + 4 - 9 - 1 - 5 + 68 + 9)^3 \\
 & := (3063 - 4 - 9 + 1 - 5 - 6 + 89)^3 \\
 \mathbf{30693697091} & := (3069 + 36 + 9 + 7 + 09 + 1)^3 \\
 & := (3069 + 3 + 6 - 9 + 70 - 9 + 1)^3 \\
 & := (3069 - 3 - 6 + 9 + 70 - 9 + 1)^3 \\
 & := (3069 - 3 - 6 - 9 + 70 + 9 + 1)^3 \\
 \mathbf{30723115968} & := (-3 + 07 + 2 + 3115 + 9 - 6 + 8)^3 \\
 & := (3 + 07 + 2 + 3115 - 9 + 6 + 8)^3 \\
 & := (3 - 07 - 2 + 3115 + 9 + 6 + 8)^3 \\
 & := (3072 + 31 + 1 + 5 + 9 + 6 + 8)^3 \\
 & := (3072 + 3 + 1 - 1 + 59 + 6 - 8)^3 \\
 & := (3072 + 3 - 1 + 1 + 59 + 6 - 8)^3 \\
 & := (3072 - 3 + 1 + 1 + 59 - 6 + 8)^3 \\
 & := (3072 - 3 + 1 - 15 + 9 + 68)^3 \\
 & := (30 - 72 + 3115 - 9 + 68)^3 \\
 & := (3072 - 31 + 159 - 68)^3 \\
 \mathbf{30752553637} & := (3075 - 2 + 55 + 3 + 6 + 3 - 7)^3 \\
 & := (3075 + 2 + 55 + 3 - 6 - 3 + 7)^3 \\
 & := (3075 + 2 + 55 - 3 - 6 + 3 + 7)^3 \\
 & := (3075 - 2 + 5 + 53 + 6 + 3 - 7)^3 \\
 & := (3075 + 2 + 5 + 53 - 6 - 3 + 7)^3 \\
 & := (3075 + 2 + 5 + 5 + 36 + 3 + 7)^3 \\
 & := (3075 + 2 + 5 + 5 + 3 + 6 + 37)^3 \\
 & := (3075 + 25 + 5 - 3 - 6 + 37)^3 \\
 & := (3075 + 2 + 55 - 36 + 37)^3 \\
 \mathbf{30811485375} & := (3081 + 1 + 4 + 8 + 53 - 7 - 5)^3 \\
 & := (3081 - 1 - 4 + 8 + 53 - 7 + 5)^3 \\
 & := (3081 + 1 - 4 - 8 + 53 + 7 + 5)^3 \\
 & := (3081 - 1 - 4 - 8 - 5 - 3 + 75)^3 \\
 \mathbf{30821664721} & := (3 + 08 + 2 + 1 - 66 + 472 - 1)^4 \\
 & := (3 + 08 + 2 - 1 - 66 + 472 + 1)^4 \\
 & := (308 + 2 - 1 + 66 + 47 - 2 - 1)^4 \\
 & := (308 - 2 - 1 + 66 + 47 + 2 - 1)^4 \\
 & := (308 - 2 + 1 + 66 + 47 - 2 + 1)^4 \\
 & := (-3 - 08 - 216 + 647 - 2 + 1)^4 \\
 & := (308 + 21 + 66 - 4 + 7 + 21)^4 \\
 & := (3 + 0821 + 66 - 472 + 1)^4 \\
 & := (30 + 82 - 166 + 472 + 1)^4 \\
 & := (-30 + 8 - 216 - 64 + 721)^4 \\
 \mathbf{30840979456} & := (30 + 8 + 4 + 09 - 7 + 9 + 4 + 5 - 6)^6 \\
 & := (30 + 8 - 4 + 09 + 7 + 9 - 4 - 5 + 6)^6 \\
 & := (30 - 8 + 4 + 09 + 7 + 9 + 4 - 5 + 6)^6 \\
 & := (30 + 8 + 4 + 09 + 7 - 9 - 4 + 5 + 6)^6 \\
 & := (30 + 8 + 4 - 09 + 7 + 9 - 4 + 5 + 6)^6 \\
 & := (30 + 8 - 4 + 09 + 7 - 9 + 4 + 5 + 6)^6 \\
 & := (30 + 8 - 4 - 09 + 7 + 9 + 4 + 5 + 6)^6 \\
 & := (-3 + 08 - 4 - 09 + 79 - 4 - 5 - 6)^6 \\
 & := (-3 - 08 + 4 - 09 + 79 + 4 - 5 - 6)^6 \\
 & := (3 - 08 - 4 - 09 + 79 - 4 + 5 - 6)^6 \\
 & := (3 + 08 + 4 - 09 + 7 - 9 - 4 + 56)^6 \\
 & := (-3 - 08 + 4 + 09 - 7 + 9 - 4 + 56)^6 \\
 & := (3 + 08 - 4 - 09 + 7 - 9 + 4 + 56)^6 \\
 & := (-3 - 08 - 4 + 09 - 7 + 9 + 4 + 56)^6 \\
 & := (-30 + 84 + 09 + 7 - 9 - 4 + 5 - 6)^6 \\
 & := (-30 + 84 - 09 + 7 + 9 - 4 + 5 - 6)^6 \\
 & := (30 + 8 + 40 + 9 - 7 - 9 - 4 - 5 - 6)^6
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} &:= (30 + 8 + 40 - 9 - 7 + 9 - 4 - 5 - 6)^6 \\ &:= (30 + 8 + 40 - 9 - 7 - 9 + 4 + 5 - 6)^6 \\ &:= (30 - 8 + 40 - 9 + 7 - 9 + 4 - 5 + 6)^6 \\ &:= (30 + 8 + 4 - 09 - 7 - 9 + 45 - 6)^6 \\ &:= (-3 + 08 - 40 + 97 + 9 - 4 - 5 - 6)^6 \\ &:= (3 - 08 - 40 + 97 + 9 - 4 + 5 - 6)^6 \\ &:= (-3 + 08 - 40 + 97 - 9 + 4 + 5 - 6)^6 \\ &:= (3 + 08 - 40 + 97 - 9 - 4 - 5 + 6)^6 \\ &:= (-3 + 08 - 40 + 9 + 79 + 4 + 5 - 6)^6 \\ &:= (3 + 08 - 40 + 9 + 79 - 4 - 5 + 6)^6 \\ &:= (3 + 08 - 40 - 9 + 79 + 4 + 5 + 6)^6 \\ &:= (3 + 08 - 40 + 9 - 7 + 94 - 5 - 6)^6 \\ &:= (-3 + 08 - 40 - 9 + 7 + 94 + 5 - 6)^6 \\ &:= (-3 - 08 - 40 + 9 - 7 + 94 + 5 + 6)^6 \\ &:= (-3 - 08 + 40 - 9 - 7 - 9 - 4 + 56)^6 \\ &:= (3 + 08 - 40 + 9 + 7 + 9 + 4 + 56)^6 \\ &:= (-3 + 08 - 4 + 097 + 9 - 45 - 6)^6 \\ &:= (3 + 08 - 4 + 097 - 9 - 45 + 6)^6 \\ &:= (3 + 08 - 4 + 09 + 79 - 45 + 6)^6 \\ &:= (30 + 84 + 09 - 7 - 9 - 45 - 6)^6 \\ &:= (30 + 84 - 09 - 7 + 9 - 45 - 6)^6 \\ &:= (30 + 8 - 40 + 9 + 7 - 9 + 45 + 6)^6 \\ &:= (30 + 8 - 40 - 9 + 7 + 9 + 45 + 6)^6 \\ &:= (30 + 8 + 4 + 097 - 94 + 5 + 6)^6 \\ &:= (30 + 8 - 4 - 09 - 7 + 94 - 56)^6 \\ &:= (3 + 084 + 09 - 79 + 45 - 6)^6 \\ &:= (-30 + 84 + 097 - 94 + 5 - 6)^6 \\ &:= (-30 - 8 + 40 + 97 + 9 + 4 - 56)^6 \\ &:= (-30 - 8 + 40 + 9 + 7 + 94 - 56)^6 \\ &:= (30 + 8 + 40 + 9 + 7 - 94 + 56)^6 \\ &:= (-30 - 8 - 40 - 9 - 7 + 94 + 56)^6 \\ &:= (3 + 08 - 409 + 7 - 9 + 456)^6 \\ &:= (-308 - 4 - 097 + 9 + 456)^6 \\ &:= (-308 - 4 - 09 - 79 + 456)^6 \\ &:= (30 + 840 - 9 - 794 - 5 - 6)^6 \\ &:= (-308 + 409 - 7 - 94 + 56)^6 \\ &:= (308 - 409 + 7 + 94 + 56)^6 \\ &:= (-30 + 8 + 4097 - 945 + 6)^3 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{30870492353} &:= (3087 + 049 + 2 - 3 + 5 - 3)^3 \\ &:= (3087 - 04 + 92 - 35 - 3)^3 \\ \mathbf{30900024072} &:= (3090 - 0024 + 072)^3 \\ \mathbf{30929574619} &:= (3092 + 9 - 5 + 7 + 46 - 1 - 9)^3 \\ &:= (3092 - 9 - 5 + 7 + 46 - 1 + 9)^3 \\ &:= (3092 - 9 - 5 + 74 + 6 - 19)^3 \\ \mathbf{30959144000} &:= (3095 - 9 + 14 + 40 + 00)^3 \\ \mathbf{30988732221} &:= (3098 + 8 + 7 + 3 + 22 + 2 + 1)^3 \\ &:= (3098 + 8 + 7 + 3 + 2 + 22 + 1)^3 \\ &:= (3098 + 8 + 7 + 3 + 2 + 2 + 21)^3 \\ &:= (3 - 098 + 8 + 7 + 3222 - 1)^3 \\ &:= (30 + 9 + 8 + 873 + 2221)^3 \\ \mathbf{31018339288} &:= (3101 + 8 + 3 + 3 + 9 + 2 + 8 + 8)^3 \\ &:= (3101 + 8 + 3 + 3 - 9 + 28 + 8)^3 \\ &:= (3101 + 83 + 3 - 9 - 28 - 8)^3 \\ \mathbf{31077609984} &:= (3107 + 7 + 60 - 9 - 9 - 8 - 4)^3 \\ \mathbf{31107273625} &:= (3110 + 7 + 2 - 7 + 36 + 2 - 5)^3 \\ &:= (3110 - 7 + 2 + 7 + 36 + 2 - 5)^3 \\ \mathbf{31116960000} &:= (311 + 169 - 60 + 000)^4 \\ \mathbf{31136956136} &:= (3113 - 6 - 9 + 56 + 1 - 3 - 6)^3 \\ &:= (3113 + 6 + 9 + 5 + 6 + 13 - 6)^3 \\ &:= (3113 + 6 + 9 + 5 - 6 + 13 + 6)^3 \\ &:= (3113 - 6 + 9 + 5 + 6 + 13 + 6)^3 \\ &:= (3113 + 6 - 9 - 5 + 6 - 1 + 36)^3 \\ &:= (3113 + 6 - 9 + 5 - 6 + 1 + 36)^3 \\ &:= (3113 - 6 - 9 + 5 + 6 + 1 + 36)^3 \\ &:= (3113 + 69 - 5 + 6 - 1 - 36)^3 \\ &:= (3113 + 69 + 5 - 6 + 1 - 36)^3 \\ &:= (3113 - 6 + 9 + 5 + 61 - 36)^3 \\ &:= (3113 - 69 + 5 + 61 + 36)^3 \\ \mathbf{31166657523} &:= (3116 - 6 - 6 - 5 - 7 + 52 + 3)^3 \\ \mathbf{31196377792} &:= (3119 - 6 + 3 + 7 + 7 + 7 + 9 + 2)^3 \\ \mathbf{31226116949} &:= (3122 + 6 + 11 + 6 + 9 + 4 - 9)^3 \\ &:= (3122 + 6 + 11 + 6 - 9 + 4 + 9)^3 \\ &:= (3122 + 6 + 1 + 16 + 9 + 4 - 9)^3 \\ &:= (3122 + 6 + 1 + 16 - 9 + 4 + 9)^3 \\ \mathbf{31255875000} &:= (3125 + 5 + 8 + 7 + 5 + 000)^3 \\ \mathbf{31285651951} &:= (3128 - 5 - 65 - 1 + 95 - 1)^3 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 \mathbf{31315447808} &:= (3131 - 54 - 4 + 7 + 80 - 8)^3 &:= (-3 - 1 - 3 - 8 + 1 + 05 + 9 - 6 + 09)^{22} \\
 &:= (3131 - 5 - 44 + 78 - 08)^3 &:= (3 - 1 - 3 - 8 + 1 + 05 + 9 - 6 + 09)^{11} \\
 &:= (-3 - 1315 + 4478 - 08)^3 &:= (-3 - 1 + 3 - 8 + 1 + 05 + 9 - 6 + 09)^{11} \\
 \mathbf{31345262577} &:= (3134 - 52 + 62 - 5 + 7 + 7)^3 &:= (-3 + 1 - 3 + 8 - 1 - 05 - 9 + 6 + 09)^{22} \\
 &:= (3134 + 52 + 6 - 25 - 7 - 7)^3 &:= (3 + 1 - 3 + 8 - 1 - 05 - 9 + 6 + 09)^{11} \\
 &:= (3134 + 5 + 2 + 62 - 57 + 7)^3 &:= (-3 + 1 + 3 + 8 - 1 - 05 - 9 + 6 + 09)^{11} \\
 \mathbf{31375096264} &:= (3137 + 50 - 9 + 6 - 26 - 4)^3 &:= (-3 - 1 - 3 + 8 + 1 - 05 - 9 + 6 + 09)^{22} \\
 \mathbf{31381059609} &:= (3 + 1 + 3 + 8 - 1 - 05 + 9 - 6 - 09)^{22} &:= (3 - 1 - 3 + 8 + 1 - 05 - 9 + 6 + 09)^{11} \\
 &:= (3 - 1 + 3 + 8 + 1 - 05 + 9 - 6 - 09)^{22} &:= (-3 - 1 + 3 + 8 + 1 - 05 - 9 + 6 + 09)^{11} \\
 &:= (-3 + 1 - 3 + 8 + 1 + 05 + 9 - 6 - 09)^{22} &:= (3 + 1 - 3 - 8 - 1 + 05 - 9 + 6 + 09)^{22} \\
 &:= (3 + 1 - 3 + 8 + 1 + 05 + 9 - 6 - 09)^{11} &:= (-3 + 1 + 3 - 8 - 1 + 05 - 9 + 6 + 09)^{22} \\
 &:= (-3 + 1 + 3 + 8 + 1 + 05 + 9 - 6 - 09)^{11} &:= (3 + 1 + 3 - 8 - 1 + 05 - 9 + 6 + 09)^{11} \\
 &:= (3 + 1 - 3 + 8 + 1 + 05 - 9 + 6 - 09)^{22} &:= (3 - 1 - 3 - 8 + 1 + 05 - 9 + 6 + 09)^{22} \\
 &:= (-3 + 1 + 3 + 8 + 1 + 05 - 9 + 6 - 09)^{22} &:= (-3 - 1 + 3 - 8 + 1 + 05 - 9 + 6 + 09)^{22} \\
 &:= (3 + 1 + 3 + 8 + 1 + 05 - 9 + 6 - 09)^{11} &:= (3 - 1 + 3 - 8 + 1 + 05 - 9 + 6 + 09)^{11} \\
 &:= (-3 + 1 - 3 + 8 - 1 - 05 + 9 + 6 - 09)^{22} &:= (-3 - 1 - 3 - 8 - 1 - 05 + 9 + 6 + 09)^{22} \\
 &:= (3 + 1 - 3 + 8 - 1 - 05 + 9 + 6 - 09)^{11} &:= (3 - 1 - 3 - 8 - 1 - 05 + 9 + 6 + 09)^{11} \\
 &:= (-3 + 1 + 3 + 8 - 1 - 05 + 9 + 6 - 09)^{11} &:= (-3 - 1 + 3 - 8 - 1 - 05 + 9 + 6 + 09)^{11} \\
 &:= (-3 - 1 - 3 + 8 + 1 - 05 + 9 + 6 - 09)^{22} &:= (-31 + 38 + 1 - 05 + 9 + 6 - 09)^{11} \\
 &:= (3 - 1 - 3 + 8 + 1 - 05 + 9 + 6 - 09)^{11} &:= (31 - 38 - 1 + 05 + 9 + 6 - 09)^{22} \\
 &:= (-3 - 1 + 3 + 8 + 1 - 05 + 9 + 6 - 09)^{11} &:= (31 - 38 - 1 + 05 + 9 - 6 + 09)^{11} \\
 &:= (3 + 1 - 3 - 8 - 1 + 05 + 9 + 6 - 09)^{22} &:= (-31 + 38 + 1 - 05 - 9 + 6 + 09)^{11} \\
 &:= (-3 + 1 + 3 - 8 - 1 + 05 + 9 + 6 - 09)^{22} &:= (31 - 38 - 1 + 05 - 9 + 6 + 09)^{22} \\
 &:= (3 + 1 + 3 - 8 - 1 + 05 + 9 + 6 - 09)^{11} &:= (31 + 3 + 8 - 10 - 5 - 9 - 6 - 09)^{22} \\
 &:= (3 - 1 - 3 - 8 + 1 + 05 + 9 + 6 - 09)^{22} &:= (31 - 3 - 8 - 10 + 5 + 9 - 6 - 09)^{11} \\
 &:= (-3 - 1 + 3 - 8 + 1 + 05 + 9 + 6 - 09)^{22} &:= (31 - 3 + 8 - 10 - 5 - 9 + 6 - 09)^{11} \\
 &:= (3 - 1 + 3 - 8 + 1 + 05 + 9 + 6 - 09)^{11} &:= (31 - 3 - 8 - 10 + 5 - 9 + 6 - 09)^{22} \\
 &:= (3 + 1 + 3 + 8 - 1 - 05 - 9 - 6 + 09)^{22} &:= (31 + 3 - 8 - 10 + 5 - 9 + 6 - 09)^{11} \\
 &:= (3 - 1 + 3 + 8 + 1 - 05 - 9 - 6 + 09)^{22} &:= (31 - 3 - 8 - 10 + 5 - 9 - 6 + 09)^{11} \\
 &:= (-3 + 1 - 3 + 8 + 1 + 05 - 9 - 6 + 09)^{22} &:= (-31 - 3 + 8 + 10 - 5 + 9 + 6 + 09)^{22} \\
 &:= (3 + 1 - 3 + 8 + 1 + 05 - 9 - 6 + 09)^{11} &:= (-31 + 3 + 8 + 10 - 5 + 9 + 6 + 09)^{11} \\
 &:= (-3 + 1 + 3 + 8 + 1 + 05 - 9 - 6 + 09)^{11} &:= (-31 + 3 - 8 + 10 + 5 + 9 + 6 + 09)^{22} \\
 &:= (3 - 1 + 3 - 8 - 1 - 05 + 9 - 6 + 09)^{22} &:= (-31 - 3 - 8 + 1 + 059 - 6 - 09)^{22} \\
 &:= (-3 + 1 - 3 + 8 - 1 - 05 + 9 - 6 + 09)^{11} &:= (-31 + 3 - 8 + 1 + 059 - 6 - 09)^{11} \\
 &:= (-3 - 1 - 3 + 8 + 1 - 05 + 9 - 6 + 09)^{11} &:= (-3 + 13 + 8 + 10 + 5 - 9 - 6 - 09)^{11} \\
 &:= (-3 + 1 - 3 - 8 - 1 + 05 + 9 - 6 + 09)^{22} &:= (3 + 13 + 8 - 10 - 5 + 9 - 6 - 09)^{22} \\
 &:= (3 + 1 - 3 - 8 - 1 + 05 + 9 - 6 + 09)^{11} &:= (-3 + 13 + 8 - 10 - 5 + 9 + 6 - 09)^{11} \\
 &:= (-3 + 1 + 3 - 8 - 1 + 05 + 9 - 6 + 09)^{11} &:= (-3 - 13 + 8 + 10 - 5 + 9 + 6 - 09)^{22}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 &:= (3 - 13 + 8 + 10 - 5 + 9 + 6 - 09)^{11} & &:= (-31 + 3 + 81 - 059 + 6 + 09)^{11} \\
 &:= (-3 + 13 - 8 - 10 + 5 + 9 + 6 - 09)^{22} & &:= (31 - 3 + 81 + 05 - 96 - 09)^{11} \\
 &:= (3 + 13 - 8 - 10 + 5 + 9 + 6 - 09)^{11} & &:= (-31 - 3 - 8 - 10 - 5 + 9 + 60 - 9)^{22} \\
 &:= (3 - 13 - 8 + 10 + 5 + 9 + 6 - 09)^{22} & &:= (-31 + 3 - 8 - 10 - 5 + 9 + 60 - 9)^{11} \\
 &:= (3 + 13 + 8 - 10 - 5 - 9 - 6 + 09)^{22} & &:= (31 - 3 + 8 + 10 + 5 + 9 - 60 + 9)^{11} \\
 &:= (-3 - 13 + 8 + 10 - 5 + 9 - 6 + 09)^{11} & &:= (-31 - 3 - 8 - 10 - 5 - 9 + 60 + 9)^{22} \\
 &:= (-3 + 13 - 8 - 10 + 5 + 9 - 6 + 09)^{11} & &:= (-31 + 3 - 8 - 10 - 5 - 9 + 60 + 9)^{11} \\
 &:= (-3 - 13 - 8 + 10 + 5 + 9 - 6 + 09)^{22} & &:= (31 - 3 - 8 - 1 + 059 - 60 - 9)^{11} \\
 &:= (3 - 13 - 8 + 10 + 5 + 9 - 6 + 09)^{11} & &:= (-3 - 13 + 81 - 059 + 6 - 09)^{22} \\
 &:= (-3 + 13 + 8 - 10 - 5 - 9 + 6 + 09)^{11} & &:= (3 - 13 + 81 - 059 + 6 - 09)^{11} \\
 &:= (-3 - 13 + 8 + 10 - 5 - 9 + 6 + 09)^{22} & &:= (-3 - 13 + 81 - 059 - 6 + 09)^{11} \\
 &:= (3 - 13 + 8 + 10 - 5 - 9 + 6 + 09)^{11} & &:= (-3 + 13 - 81 + 059 + 6 + 09)^{22} \\
 &:= (-3 + 13 - 8 - 10 + 5 - 9 + 6 + 09)^{22} & &:= (3 + 13 - 81 + 059 + 6 + 09)^{11} \\
 &:= (3 + 13 - 8 - 10 + 5 - 9 + 6 + 09)^{11} & &:= (-3 + 13 + 81 + 05 - 96 + 09)^{11} \\
 &:= (3 - 13 - 8 + 10 + 5 - 9 + 6 + 09)^{22} & &:= (-3 - 13 - 81 - 05 + 96 + 09)^{22} \\
 &:= (3 + 1 + 38 - 10 - 5 - 9 - 6 - 09)^{22} & &:= (3 - 13 - 81 - 05 + 96 + 09)^{11} \\
 &:= (-3 + 1 + 38 - 10 - 5 - 9 + 6 - 09)^{11} & &:= (-3 - 13 - 8 - 10 - 5 - 9 + 60 - 9)^{22} \\
 &:= (3 - 1 - 38 + 10 + 5 + 9 + 6 + 09)^{22} & &:= (3 - 13 - 8 - 10 - 5 - 9 + 60 - 9)^{11} \\
 &:= (-3 + 1 - 38 - 1 + 059 - 6 - 09)^{22} & &:= (-3 + 13 + 8 + 1 + 059 - 60 - 9)^{11} \\
 &:= (3 + 1 - 38 - 1 + 059 - 6 - 09)^{11} & &:= (-3 + 13 + 8 - 1 - 059 + 60 - 9)^{11} \\
 &:= (-3 - 1 - 38 + 1 + 059 - 6 - 09)^{22} & &:= (-3 + 13 - 8 - 1 + 059 - 60 + 9)^{11} \\
 &:= (3 - 1 - 38 + 1 + 059 - 6 - 09)^{11} & &:= (-3 - 13 + 8 + 1 - 059 + 60 + 9)^{22} \\
 &:= (3 - 1 + 3 + 81 - 05 - 9 - 60 - 9)^{22} & &:= (3 - 13 + 8 + 1 - 059 + 60 + 9)^{11} \\
 &:= (-3 + 1 - 3 + 81 + 05 - 9 - 60 - 9)^{22} & &:= (3 + 1 - 38 - 10 + 5 - 9 + 60 - 9)^{22} \\
 &:= (3 + 1 - 3 + 81 + 05 - 9 - 60 - 9)^{11} & &:= (-3 - 1 - 38 - 10 - 5 + 9 + 60 - 9)^{22} \\
 &:= (-3 + 1 + 3 + 81 + 05 - 9 - 60 - 9)^{11} & &:= (3 - 1 - 38 - 10 - 5 + 9 + 60 - 9)^{11} \\
 &:= (-3 - 1 - 3 + 81 - 05 + 9 - 60 - 9)^{11} & &:= (3 - 1 + 38 + 10 - 5 + 9 - 60 + 9)^{22} \\
 &:= (-3 - 1 - 3 + 81 - 05 - 9 - 60 + 9)^{11} & &:= (-3 + 1 + 38 + 10 + 5 + 9 - 60 + 9)^{11} \\
 &:= (3 + 1 - 3 - 81 + 05 + 9 + 60 + 9)^{22} & &:= (-3 - 1 - 38 - 10 - 5 - 9 + 60 + 9)^{22} \\
 &:= (-3 + 1 + 3 - 81 + 05 + 9 + 60 + 9)^{22} & &:= (3 - 1 - 38 - 10 - 5 - 9 + 60 + 9)^{11} \\
 &:= (3 + 1 + 3 - 81 + 05 + 9 + 60 + 9)^{11} & &:= (-3 + 1 - 3 + 8 + 105 - 96 - 09)^{22} \\
 &:= (31 + 38 - 1 - 05 + 9 - 60 - 9)^{22} & &:= (3 + 1 - 3 + 8 + 105 - 96 - 09)^{11} \\
 &:= (31 + 38 - 1 - 05 - 9 - 60 + 9)^{22} & &:= (-3 + 1 + 3 + 8 + 105 - 96 - 09)^{11} \\
 &:= (-31 - 38 - 1 - 05 + 9 + 60 + 9)^{22} & &:= (-3 - 1 - 3 - 8 + 105 - 96 + 09)^{22} \\
 &:= (31 - 3 - 81 + 059 + 6 - 09)^{22} & &:= (3 - 1 - 3 - 8 + 105 - 96 + 09)^{11} \\
 &:= (31 + 3 - 81 + 059 + 6 - 09)^{11} & &:= (-3 - 1 + 3 - 8 + 105 - 96 + 09)^{11} \\
 &:= (31 - 3 - 81 + 059 - 6 + 09)^{11} & &:= (-3 + 1 - 3 + 8 - 105 + 96 + 09)^{22} \\
 &:= (-31 - 3 + 81 - 059 + 6 + 09)^{22} & &:= (3 + 1 - 3 + 8 - 105 + 96 + 09)^{11}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 &:= (-3 + 1 + 3 + 8 - 105 + 96 + 09)^{11} \\
 &:= (-3 + 1 - 3 + 8 + 10 + 59 - 60 - 9)^{22} \\
 &:= (3 + 1 - 3 + 8 + 10 + 59 - 60 - 9)^{11} \\
 &:= (-3 + 1 + 3 + 8 + 10 + 59 - 60 - 9)^{11} \\
 &:= (-3 - 1 - 3 + 8 + 10 - 59 + 60 - 9)^{22} \\
 &:= (3 - 1 - 3 + 8 + 10 - 59 + 60 - 9)^{11} \\
 &:= (-3 - 1 + 3 + 8 + 10 - 59 + 60 - 9)^{11} \\
 &:= (-3 - 1 - 3 - 8 + 10 + 59 - 60 + 9)^{22} \\
 &:= (3 - 1 - 3 - 8 + 10 + 59 - 60 + 9)^{11} \\
 &:= (-3 - 1 + 3 - 8 + 10 + 59 - 60 + 9)^{11} \\
 &:= (-3 + 1 - 3 + 8 - 10 - 59 + 60 + 9)^{22} \\
 &:= (3 + 1 - 3 + 8 - 10 - 59 + 60 + 9)^{11} \\
 &:= (-3 + 1 + 3 + 8 - 10 - 59 + 60 + 9)^{11} \\
 &:= (31 + 38 - 10 - 59 - 6 + 09)^{22} \\
 &:= (-31 - 38 + 10 + 59 - 6 + 09)^{22} \\
 &:= (-31 - 38 - 10 - 5 + 96 - 09)^{22} \\
 &:= (-31 - 3 - 8 + 105 + 9 - 60 - 9)^{22} \\
 &:= (-31 + 3 - 8 + 105 + 9 - 60 - 9)^{11} \\
 &:= (-31 - 3 - 8 + 105 - 9 - 60 + 9)^{22} \\
 &:= (-31 + 3 - 8 + 105 - 9 - 60 + 9)^{11} \\
 &:= (31 - 3 + 8 - 105 + 9 + 60 + 9)^{11} \\
 &:= (-3 - 13 - 8 + 105 - 9 - 60 - 9)^{22} \\
 &:= (3 - 13 - 8 + 105 - 9 - 60 - 9)^{11} \\
 &:= (-3 - 1 - 38 + 105 + 9 - 60 - 9)^{22} \\
 &:= (3 - 1 - 38 + 105 + 9 - 60 - 9)^{11} \\
 &:= (-3 - 1 - 38 + 105 - 9 - 60 + 9)^{22} \\
 &:= (3 - 1 - 38 + 105 - 9 - 60 + 9)^{11} \\
 &:= (-3 + 1 + 38 - 105 + 9 + 60 + 9)^{11} \\
 &:= (-31 + 38 + 10 - 59 + 60 - 9)^{11} \\
 &:= (3 + 138 - 10 - 59 - 60 - 9)^{22} \\
 &:= (3 - 138 + 10 + 59 + 60 + 9)^{22} \\
 \mathbf{31404948875} &:= (3140 + 4 + 9 + 4 + 8 - 8 - 7 + 5)^3 \\
 &:= (3140 + 4 + 9 + 4 - 8 + 8 - 7 + 5)^3 \\
 &:= (3140 - 4 + 9 - 4 + 8 + 8 - 7 + 5)^3 \\
 &:= (3140 - 4 - 9 + 48 - 8 - 7 - 5)^3 \\
 &:= (3140 - 4 + 94 + 8 - 8 - 75)^3 \\
 &:= (3140 - 4 + 94 - 8 + 8 - 75)^3 \\
 &:= (3 - 1 + 4049 - 4 - 887 - 5)^3
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 &:= (3140 + 49 + 48 - 87 + 5)^3 \\
 &:= (-31 + 4049 + 4 + 8 - 875)^3 \\
 \mathbf{31414372081} &:= (3 + 1 + 414 + 3 + 7 + 2 - 08 - 1)^4 \\
 &:= (-3 + 1 + 414 - 3 + 7 - 2 + 08 - 1)^4 \\
 &:= (3 - 1 + 414 + 3 - 7 + 2 + 08 - 1)^4 \\
 &:= (3 - 1 + 414 + 3 + 7 + 2 - 08 + 1)^4 \\
 &:= (3 + 1 + 414 + 3 - 7 - 2 + 08 + 1)^4 \\
 &:= (-3 - 1 + 414 - 3 + 7 - 2 + 08 + 1)^4 \\
 &:= (-3 + 1 - 4 + 1 + 437 - 2 - 08 - 1)^4 \\
 &:= (-3 - 1 - 4 - 1 + 437 + 2 - 08 - 1)^4 \\
 &:= (-3 + 1 - 4 - 1 + 437 - 2 - 08 + 1)^4 \\
 &:= (-3 - 1 - 4 + 1 + 437 - 2 - 08 + 1)^4 \\
 &:= (31 + 4 + 1 + 4 + 372 + 08 + 1)^4 \\
 &:= (3 + 1 + 414 - 3 - 7 + 20 - 8 + 1)^4 \\
 &:= (-3 + 1 + 414 + 3 - 7 + 20 - 8 + 1)^4 \\
 &:= (3 - 1 - 4 - 1 + 437 - 20 + 8 - 1)^4 \\
 &:= (-3 + 1 - 4 + 1 + 437 - 20 + 8 + 1)^4 \\
 &:= (314 + 14 + 3 + 7 + 2 + 081)^4 \\
 &:= (314 + 1 + 43 + 72 - 08 - 1)^4 \\
 &:= (314 - 1 + 43 + 72 - 08 + 1)^4 \\
 &:= (-314 + 1 + 4 + 3 + 720 + 8 - 1)^4 \\
 &:= (-314 - 1 + 4 + 3 + 720 + 8 + 1)^4 \\
 &:= (-31 + 4 - 1 - 4 + 372 + 081)^4 \\
 &:= (-31 - 4 - 1 + 4 + 372 + 081)^4 \\
 &:= (-3 + 1 - 41 + 437 + 20 + 8 - 1)^4 \\
 &:= (-3 - 1 - 41 + 437 + 20 + 8 + 1)^4 \\
 &:= (314 + 143 - 7 - 20 - 8 - 1)^4 \\
 &:= (31 + 414 - 37 + 20 - 8 + 1)^4 \\
 &:= (3 + 1 + 41 + 437 + 20 - 81)^4 \\
 &:= (31 + 414 + 37 + 20 - 81)^4 \\
 &:= (31 - 414 + 3 + 720 + 81)^4 \\
 \mathbf{31434820416} &:= (3143 + 4 + 8 + 2 + 04 + 1 - 6)^3 \\
 &:= (3143 + 4 + 8 - 2 - 04 + 1 + 6)^3 \\
 &:= (3143 - 4 + 8 - 2 + 04 + 1 + 6)^3 \\
 &:= (3143 - 4 + 8 + 20 - 4 - 1 - 6)^3 \\
 &:= (3143 + 4 - 8 + 20 + 4 - 1 - 6)^3 \\
 &:= (-314 + 3482 + 04 - 16)^3 \\
 \mathbf{31464710893} &:= (3146 - 4 + 7 + 10 - 8 + 9 - 3)^3
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 &:= (3146 + 4 - 7 + 10 - 8 + 9 + 3)^3 & &:= (3 + 17 - 1 + 391 + 1 + 05 + 6)^4 \\
 &:= (3146 - 4 - 71 + 089 - 3)^3 & &:= (3 + 1 + 7 - 1 + 391 + 10 + 5 + 6)^4 \\
 \mathbf{31494620312} &:= (3149 - 4 + 6 - 2 - 03 + 12)^3 & &:= (3 - 1 + 7 + 1 + 391 + 10 + 5 + 6)^4 \\
 &:= (3149 + 4 - 6 + 2 - 03 + 12)^3 & &:= (317 + 1 - 3 + 9 - 1 + 105 - 6)^4 \\
 &:= (3149 + 4 - 6 + 20 + 3 - 12)^3 & &:= (317 - 1 - 3 + 9 + 1 + 105 - 6)^4 \\
 \mathbf{31524548679} &:= (3152 + 4 - 5 - 4 + 8 + 6 + 7 - 9)^3 & &:= (317 + 1 + 3 - 9 - 1 + 105 + 6)^4 \\
 &:= (3152 - 4 - 5 + 4 + 8 + 6 + 7 - 9)^3 & &:= (317 - 1 + 3 - 9 + 1 + 105 + 6)^4 \\
 &:= (3152 + 4 - 5 + 4 + 8 - 6 - 7 + 9)^3 & &:= (317 + 13 + 91 - 10 + 5 + 6)^4 \\
 &:= (3152 + 4 + 5 - 4 - 8 - 6 + 7 + 9)^3 & &:= (317 - 13 + 9 + 110 + 5 - 6)^4 \\
 &:= (3152 - 4 + 5 + 4 - 8 - 6 + 7 + 9)^3 & &:= (317 - 1 + 39 + 11 + 056)^4 \\
 &:= (3152 - 45 + 48 + 6 + 7 - 9)^3 & &:= (317 + 1 + 39 - 1 + 10 + 56)^4 \\
 &:= (3152 + 45 - 48 - 6 + 7 + 9)^3 & &:= (317 - 1 + 39 + 1 + 10 + 56)^4 \\
 &:= (3152 - 4 - 54 - 8 - 6 + 79)^3 & &:= (-31 + 71 + 391 - 10 - 5 + 6)^4 \\
 &:= (3 + 15 + 2454 + 8 + 679)^3 & &:= (3 - 17 - 1 + 391 - 10 + 56)^4 \\
 \mathbf{31554496000} &:= (3155 + 4 + 4 - 9 + 6 + 000)^3 & &\mathbf{31734578296} := (3173 + 4 + 5 - 7 + 8 - 2 - 9 - 6)^3 \\
 \mathbf{31584462281} &:= (3158 + 4 + 4 + 6 - 2 - 2 - 8 + 1)^3 & &:= (3173 - 4 - 5 + 7 + 8 + 2 - 9 - 6)^3 \\
 &:= (3158 + 4 - 4 + 6 + 2 + 2 - 8 + 1)^3 & &:= (3173 - 4 - 5 - 7 + 8 - 2 + 9 - 6)^3 \\
 &:= (3158 - 4 + 4 + 6 + 2 + 2 - 8 + 1)^3 & &:= (3173 + 4 - 5 + 7 - 8 - 2 - 9 + 6)^3 \\
 &:= (3158 - 4 - 4 + 6 - 2 - 2 + 8 + 1)^3 & &:= (3173 + 4 + 5 - 7 - 8 + 2 - 9 + 6)^3 \\
 &:= (3158 + 4 - 4 - 6 + 2 - 2 + 8 + 1)^3 & &:= (3173 - 4 - 5 - 7 - 8 + 2 + 9 + 6)^3 \\
 &:= (3158 - 4 + 4 - 6 + 2 - 2 + 8 + 1)^3 & &:= (3173 - 4 + 5 + 7 + 8 - 29 + 6)^3 \\
 &:= (3158 + 4 - 4 - 6 - 2 + 2 + 8 + 1)^3 & &:= (3173 - 45 + 7 + 8 + 29 - 6)^3 \\
 &:= (3158 - 4 + 4 - 6 - 2 + 2 + 8 + 1)^3 & &:= (3173 + 4 + 5 + 78 + 2 - 96)^3 \\
 \mathbf{31614447528} &:= (3161 + 44 + 4 - 75 + 28)^3 & &:= (3 + 1 - 7 + 3457 + 8 - 296)^3 \\
 &:= (3161 + 4 + 44 - 75 + 28)^3 & &\mathbf{31757969376} := (3 + 1 + 75 + 7 + 9 + 6 + 9 + 3 + 7 + 6)^5 \\
 \mathbf{31644451747} &:= (3164 + 4 + 4 + 5 - 17 - 4 + 7)^3 & &:= (3 + 1 + 7 + 5 + 79 + 6 + 9 + 3 + 7 + 6)^5 \\
 &:= (3164 + 4 - 4 + 5 - 17 + 4 + 7)^3 & &:= (3 + 1 + 7 + 5 + 7 + 96 + 9 - 3 + 7 - 6)^5 \\
 &:= (3164 - 4 + 4 + 5 - 17 + 4 + 7)^3 & &:= (-3 + 1 + 7 + 5 + 7 + 96 + 9 + 3 + 7 - 6)^5 \\
 \mathbf{31704517125} &:= (3170 + 4 + 5 + 1 - 7 - 1 - 2 - 5)^3 & &:= (3 - 1 + 7 - 5 + 7 + 96 + 9 - 3 + 7 + 6)^5 \\
 &:= (3170 + 4 + 5 - 1 - 7 + 1 - 2 - 5)^3 & &:= (3 + 1 + 7 + 5 + 7 + 96 - 9 + 3 + 7 + 6)^5 \\
 &:= (3170 - 4 - 5 + 1 + 7 - 1 + 2 - 5)^3 & &:= (-3 - 1 + 7 - 5 + 7 + 96 + 9 + 3 + 7 + 6)^5 \\
 &:= (3170 - 4 - 5 - 1 + 7 + 1 + 2 - 5)^3 & &:= (-3 + 1 + 7 + 5 + 7 + 9 + 6 + 93 + 7 - 6)^5 \\
 &:= (3170 - 4 + 5 - 1 - 7 - 1 - 2 + 5)^3 & &:= (-3 + 1 + 7 + 5 + 7 + 9 - 6 + 93 + 7 + 6)^5 \\
 &:= (3170 + 4 - 5 + 1 - 7 - 1 - 2 + 5)^3 & &:= (3 + 1 + 7 + 5 + 7 - 9 + 6 + 93 + 7 + 6)^5 \\
 &:= (3170 + 4 - 5 - 1 - 7 + 1 - 2 + 5)^3 & &:= (-3 - 1 + 7 - 5 + 7 + 9 + 6 + 93 + 7 + 6)^5 \\
 \mathbf{31713911056} &:= (317 + 1 + 3 + 91 - 1 + 05 + 6)^4 & &:= (3 + 1 + 7 + 5 + 7 + 9 + 6 + 9 + 3 + 76)^5 \\
 &:= (317 - 1 + 3 + 91 + 1 + 05 + 6)^4 & &:= (31 + 7 + 5 + 7 + 9 + 69 - 3 + 7 - 6)^5 \\
 &:= (3 + 17 + 1 + 391 - 1 + 05 + 6)^4 & &:= (31 + 7 + 5 + 7 - 9 + 69 + 3 + 7 + 6)^5
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{31915344448} &:= (3191 - 5 - 34 + 4 + 4 + 4 + 8)^3 \\ &:= (3191 - 5 + 34 - 44 + 4 - 8)^3 \\ &:= (3191 - 5 + 34 + 4 - 44 - 8)^3 \\ &:= (3191 - 5 + 34 + 4 - 4 - 48)^3 \\ &:= (3191 - 5 + 34 - 4 + 4 - 48)^3 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{31945538717} &:= (3194 + 5 - 5 - 3 - 8 + 7 - 17)^3 \\ &:= (3194 - 5 + 5 - 3 - 8 + 7 - 17)^3 \\ &:= (3194 + 55 + 3 - 87 + 1 + 7)^3 \\ &:= (3194 + 5 + 53 - 87 + 1 + 7)^3 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{31975752024} &:= (3197 + 5 - 7 + 5 - 20 - 2 - 4)^3 \\ &:= (3197 + 5 - 7 + 5 - 2 - 024)^3 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{32005984375} &:= (3200 - 5 - 9 + 8 - 4 - 3 - 7 - 5)^3 \\ &:= (3200 + 5 - 9 - 8 - 4 + 3 - 7 - 5)^3 \\ &:= (3200 - 5 - 9 - 8 - 4 + 3 - 7 + 5)^3 \\ &:= (3200 + 5 + 9 - 8 - 43 + 7 + 5)^3 \\ &:= (3200 + 59 - 8 - 4 + 3 - 75)^3 \\ &:= (3200 + 5 - 98 - 4 - 3 + 75)^3 \\ &:= (3200 - 5 + 98 - 43 - 75)^3 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{32015587041} &:= (320 + 1 + 5 + 5 + 87 + 04 + 1)^4 \\ &:= (320 + 15 + 5 + 8 + 70 + 4 + 1)^4 \\ &:= (-3 - 20 - 1 + 558 - 70 - 41)^4 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{32036235776} &:= (3203 + 6 + 23 - 57 + 7 - 6)^3 \\ &:= (3203 - 6 + 23 - 57 + 7 + 6)^3 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{32096795752} &:= (3209 - 6 - 7 - 9 + 5 - 7 - 5 - 2)^3 \\ &:= (3209 - 6 - 7 - 9 - 5 - 7 + 5 - 2)^3 \\ &:= (3209 - 6 - 79 + 57 - 5 + 2)^3 \\ &:= (3209 - 6 - 79 - 5 + 7 + 52)^3 \\ &:= (3209 - 6 - 7 - 95 + 75 + 2)^3 \\ &:= (3209 - 67 + 95 - 7 - 52)^3 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{32127104339} &:= (3212 - 71 - 04 + 33 + 9)^3 \\ &:= (3212 - 71 - 04 + 3 + 39)^3 \\ &:= (3 + 2127 + 1043 - 3 + 9)^3 \\ &:= (-3 + 2127 + 1043 + 3 + 9)^3 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{32157432000} &:= (-3 - 2 + 1 - 5 - 7 - 4 + 3200 + 0)^3 \\ &:= (3215 - 7 + 4 - 32 + 000)^3 \\ &:= (3 - 21 - 5 + 7 - 4 + 3200 + 0)^3 \\ &:= (-32 + 15 - 7 + 4 + 3200 + 0)^3 \\ &:= (32 + 1 - 57 + 4 + 3200 + 0)^3 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{32218144568} &:= (3221 + 8 + 1 + 4 - 4 - 56 + 8)^3 \\ &:= (3221 + 8 + 1 - 4 + 4 - 56 + 8)^3 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{32248529487} &:= (3224 + 8 - 5 + 2 + 9 - 48 - 7)^3 \\ &:= (3224 - 85 - 2 - 9 + 48 + 7)^3 \\ &:= (3224 + 8 + 5 + 29 + 4 - 87)^3 \\ &:= (-3 + 2248 - 5 + 2 + 948 - 7)^3 \\ &:= (-3 + 2 + 248 - 5 + 2948 - 7)^3 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{32278933504} &:= (3227 + 8 - 9 - 33 - 5 - 04)^3 \\ &:= (3227 + 8 - 9 - 3 - 35 - 04)^3 \\ &:= (3227 + 8 + 9 - 3 - 3 - 50 - 4)^3 \\ &:= (3227 - 89 + 3 - 3 + 50 - 4)^3 \\ &:= (3227 - 89 - 3 + 3 + 50 - 4)^3 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{32309356625} &:= (3230 + 9 - 35 - 6 - 6 - 2 - 5)^3 \\ &:= (3230 + 9 + 3 - 56 + 6 - 2 - 5)^3 \\ &:= (3 + 2 + 3093 + 56 + 6 + 25)^3 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{32319410176} &:= (3 - 2 + 3 + 1 + 9 + 410 - 1 + 7 - 6)^4 \\ &:= (3 - 2 + 3 - 1 + 9 + 410 + 1 + 7 - 6)^4 \\ &:= (3 + 2 - 3 + 1 + 9 + 410 + 1 + 7 - 6)^4 \\ &:= (-3 + 2 + 3 + 1 + 9 + 410 + 1 + 7 - 6)^4 \\ &:= (3 + 2 + 3 - 1 + 9 + 410 - 1 - 7 + 6)^4 \\ &:= (3 - 2 + 3 + 1 + 9 + 410 + 1 - 7 + 6)^4 \\ &:= (-3 - 2 - 3 + 1 + 9 + 410 - 1 + 7 + 6)^4 \\ &:= (3 + 2 + 3 + 1 - 9 + 410 + 1 + 7 + 6)^4 \\ &:= (-3 - 2 - 3 - 1 + 9 + 410 + 1 + 7 + 6)^4 \\ &:= (-3 + 23 - 1 + 9 + 410 - 1 - 7 - 6)^4 \\ &:= (-3 + 23 + 1 - 9 + 410 + 1 + 7 - 6)^4 \\ &:= (3 + 23 - 1 - 9 + 410 - 1 - 7 + 6)^4 \\ &:= (323 + 19 + 4 + 1 + 01 + 76)^4 \\ &:= (323 - 1 + 94 + 10 - 1 - 7 + 6)^4 \\ &:= (323 + 1 + 9 + 4 + 10 + 1 + 76)^4 \\ &:= (32 + 3 - 19 + 410 - 1 - 7 + 6)^4 \\ &:= (32 - 3 - 1 + 9 + 410 - 17 - 6)^4 \\ &:= (32 + 3 - 1 - 9 + 410 - 17 + 6)^4 \\ &:= (3 + 231 + 9 + 4 + 1 + 0176)^4 \\ &:= (-3 + 2 + 319 + 4 + 101 + 7 - 6)^4 \\ &:= (3 - 2 + 319 + 4 + 101 - 7 + 6)^4 \\ &:= (-3 - 2 + 319 - 4 + 101 + 7 + 6)^4 \\ &:= (-3 + 231 + 94 + 101 + 7 - 6)^4 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 &:= (3 + 231 + 9 + 4 + 101 + 76)^4 \\
 \mathbf{32339798856} &:= (3233 + 9 + 7 + 9 - 8 - 8 - 56)^3 \\
 &:= (3233 + 9 - 7 - 9 + 8 + 8 - 56)^3 \\
 &:= (3233 - 9 - 7 + 9 + 8 + 8 - 56)^3 \\
 &:= (-3 + 2339 - 7 + 9 - 8 + 856)^3 \\
 &:= (3233 - 97 + 98 + 8 - 56)^3 \\
 \mathbf{32401800025} &:= (-32 + 40 + 180002 - 5)^2 \\
 \mathbf{32431240269} &:= (3243 + 1 + 2 - 40 - 2 - 6 - 9)^3 \\
 &:= (3243 + 1 - 2 - 40 + 2 - 6 - 9)^3 \\
 &:= (3243 + 1 + 2 - 40 - 26 + 9)^3 \\
 \mathbf{32492296871} &:= (3249 + 22 - 96 + 8 + 7 + 1)^3 \\
 &:= (3249 - 2 + 29 - 6 - 8 - 71)^3 \\
 \mathbf{32522853888} &:= (3252 - 28 - 5 - 3 - 8 - 8 - 8)^3 \\
 &:= (3252 - 2 - 85 + 3 + 8 + 8 + 8)^3 \\
 &:= (3252 + 28 + 5 + 3 - 88 - 8)^3 \\
 &:= (3252 + 28 - 5 - 3 - 88 + 8)^3 \\
 &:= (3252 + 28 + 5 + 3 - 8 - 88)^3 \\
 &:= (3252 + 28 - 5 - 3 + 8 - 88)^3 \\
 &:= (-3 + 25 + 2285 - 3 + 888)^3 \\
 \mathbf{32553430057} &:= (3255 - 34 - 30 - 05 + 7)^3 \\
 \mathbf{32584025384} &:= (3258 - 40 - 25 - 3 + 8 - 4)^3 \\
 \mathbf{32614639875} &:= (3261 - 4 - 63 - 9 + 8 + 7 - 5)^3 \\
 &:= (3261 + 4 + 6 - 3 + 9 - 87 + 5)^3 \\
 &:= (3261 - 46 + 3 - 98 + 75)^3 \\
 \mathbf{32625390625} &:= (326 + 2 + 5 + 3 + 90 + 6 - 2 - 5)^4 \\
 &:= (326 - 2 + 5 + 3 + 90 + 6 + 2 - 5)^4 \\
 &:= (326 - 2 + 5 - 3 + 90 + 6 - 2 + 5)^4 \\
 &:= (326 + 2 - 5 + 3 + 90 + 6 - 2 + 5)^4 \\
 &:= (326 - 2 - 5 + 3 + 90 + 6 + 2 + 5)^4 \\
 &:= (3 + 26 + 2 + 5 + 390 + 6 - 2 - 5)^4 \\
 &:= (3 + 26 - 2 + 5 + 390 + 6 + 2 - 5)^4 \\
 &:= (3 + 26 + 2 - 5 + 390 + 6 - 2 + 5)^4 \\
 &:= (-3 + 26 - 2 + 5 + 390 + 6 - 2 + 5)^4 \\
 &:= (3 + 26 - 2 - 5 + 390 + 6 + 2 + 5)^4 \\
 &:= (3 + 2 + 6 + 25 + 390 + 6 - 2 - 5)^4 \\
 &:= (3 - 2 + 6 + 25 + 390 + 6 + 2 - 5)^4 \\
 &:= (-3 - 2 + 6 + 25 + 390 + 6 - 2 + 5)^4 \\
 &:= (3 + 2 + 6 - 2 - 5 + 390 + 6 + 25)^4
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 &:= (3 - 2 + 6 + 2 - 5 + 390 + 6 + 25)^4 \\
 &:= (-3 - 2 + 6 - 2 + 5 + 390 + 6 + 25)^4 \\
 &:= (326 + 25 - 3 + 90 - 6 - 2 - 5)^4 \\
 &:= (326 - 2 + 53 - 9 + 062 - 5)^4 \\
 &:= (326 - 2 + 5 + 39 + 062 - 5)^4 \\
 &:= (326 - 2 - 5 + 39 + 062 + 5)^4 \\
 &:= (326 - 2 - 5 - 3 + 90 - 6 + 25)^4 \\
 &:= (-3 + 26 + 25 + 390 - 6 - 2 - 5)^4 \\
 &:= (-3 - 26 + 2 + 5 + 390 + 62 - 5)^4 \\
 &:= (-3 - 26 + 2 - 5 + 390 + 62 + 5)^4 \\
 &:= (-3 + 26 - 2 - 5 + 390 - 6 + 25)^4 \\
 &:= (3 + 2 - 62 + 539 - 062 + 5)^4 \\
 &:= (-3 + 2 + 62 + 5 + 390 - 6 - 25)^4 \\
 &:= (-3 + 2 - 6 - 25 + 390 + 62 + 5)^4 \\
 &:= (326 + 25 + 3 + 90 + 6 - 25)^4 \\
 &:= (326 - 25 + 3 + 90 + 6 + 25)^4 \\
 &:= (3 + 26 + 25 + 390 + 6 - 25)^4 \\
 &:= (3 + 26 - 25 + 390 + 6 + 25)^4 \\
 &:= (3 + 2 - 62 - 53 - 90 + 625)^4 \\
 \mathbf{32645273536} &:= (3264 + 5 - 2 - 73 + 5 + 3 - 6)^3 \\
 &:= (3264 + 5 + 2 - 73 - 5 - 3 + 6)^3 \\
 &:= (3264 - 5 + 2 - 73 + 5 - 3 + 6)^3 \\
 &:= (-326 - 4 - 5 + 2 - 7 + 3536)^3 \\
 &:= (3 + 2645 + 2 + 7 + 3 + 536)^3 \\
 &:= (3264 + 52 - 73 - 53 + 6)^3 \\
 \mathbf{32675926373} &:= (3267 - 59 + 2 - 6 + 3 - 7 - 3)^3 \\
 &:= (3267 - 59 + 2 - 6 - 3 - 7 + 3)^3 \\
 &:= (3267 + 5 + 9 - 2 - 6 - 3 - 73)^3 \\
 &:= (3267 - 5 + 9 + 2 - 6 + 3 - 73)^3 \\
 &:= (3267 + 5 - 9 - 2 + 6 + 3 - 73)^3 \\
 &:= (3267 + 5 - 9 - 26 - 37 - 3)^3 \\
 \mathbf{32706598392} &:= (3270 - 65 + 9 - 8 + 3 - 9 - 2)^3 \\
 &:= (3270 - 65 - 9 - 8 + 3 + 9 - 2)^3 \\
 &:= (3270 - 6 - 5 - 98 + 39 - 2)^3 \\
 &:= (-3 + 2706 + 5 + 98 + 392)^3 \\
 \mathbf{32737289599} &:= (3273 - 7 + 2 + 8 - 95 + 9 + 9)^3 \\
 &:= (3273 - 7 + 2 + 8 - 9 - 59 - 9)^3 \\
 &:= (3273 - 7 + 28 - 95 + 9 - 9)^3
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 & := (3273 - 7 + 28 - 95 - 9 + 9)^3 & := (32 - 9 + 335 - 3 + 8 + 57 + 6)^4 \\
 & := (3273 - 7 + 28 + 9 - 5 - 99)^3 & := (-32 - 9 + 3 - 3 + 538 + 5 - 76)^4 \\
 \mathbf{32798729601} & := (3279 - 8 - 72 + 9 - 6 - 01)^3 & := (-32 - 9 - 3 + 3 + 538 + 5 - 76)^4 \\
 & := (3279 + 8 - 72 - 9 - 6 + 01)^3 & := (3 + 293 + 35 - 3 + 85 + 7 + 6)^4 \\
 & := (3279 + 8 + 7 + 2 - 96 + 01)^3 & := (-3 + 293 + 35 + 3 + 85 + 7 + 6)^4 \\
 \mathbf{32829478408} & := (3282 + 9 - 4 + 7 - 84 - 08)^3 & := (-3 + 293 - 3 + 53 + 85 + 7 - 6)^4 \\
 & := (3282 - 9 - 47 + 8 - 40 + 8)^3 & := (-3 + 29 + 33 - 5 + 385 - 7 - 6)^4 \\
 \mathbf{32860246427} & := (3286 - 024 - 64 - 2 + 7)^3 & := (3 - 2 - 93 + 3 - 53 - 8 + 576)^4 \\
 & := (3286 - 02 - 46 - 42 + 7)^3 & := (-3 + 2 - 9 + 335 + 38 + 57 + 6)^4 \\
 \mathbf{32891033664} & := (3289 + 10 - 33 - 66 + 4)^3 & := (3 - 2 - 9 - 33 + 538 + 5 - 76)^4 \\
 \mathbf{32921840125} & := (3292 + 1 - 84 - 01 + 2 - 5)^3 & := (32 + 93 - 3 - 5 + 385 - 76)^4 \\
 & := (3292 - 1 - 84 + 01 + 2 - 5)^3 & := (-3 + 293 + 35 + 38 + 57 + 6)^4 \\
 \mathbf{32933538576} & := (329 + 3 + 3 + 5 - 3 + 8 + 5 + 76)^4 & := (3 + 2 - 93 + 353 + 85 + 76)^4 \\
 & := (329 + 3 - 3 + 5 + 3 + 8 + 5 + 76)^4 & := (-32 + 933 - 538 + 57 + 6)^4 \\
 & := (329 - 3 + 3 + 5 + 3 + 8 + 5 + 76)^4 & \mathbf{32983510743} := (3 - 298 + 3510 - 7 - 4 + 3)^3 \\
 & := (32 + 9 - 3 - 3 + 5 + 385 + 7 - 6)^4 & \mathbf{33014374912} := (3301 - 4 - 3 - 74 - 9 - 1 - 2)^3 \\
 & := (32 + 9 + 3 + 3 - 5 + 385 - 7 + 6)^4 & := (3301 + 4 + 3 - 7 - 4 - 91 + 2)^3 \\
 & := (32 - 9 + 3 - 3 + 5 + 385 + 7 + 6)^4 & := (3301 - 4 - 3 + 7 - 4 - 91 + 2)^3 \\
 & := (32 - 9 - 3 + 3 + 5 + 385 + 7 + 6)^4 & := (3301 - 4 + 3 - 7 + 4 - 91 + 2)^3 \\
 & := (-3 + 2 + 9 + 335 - 3 + 85 + 7 - 6)^4 & := (3301 - 4 - 37 - 49 - 1 - 2)^3 \\
 & := (3 - 2 + 9 + 335 - 3 + 85 - 7 + 6)^4 & \mathbf{33038369407} := (3 + 3 + 03 + 8 + 3 + 6 + 94 + 07)^5 \\
 & := (-3 - 2 + 9 + 335 + 3 + 85 - 7 + 6)^4 & := (33 + 03 + 83 + 6 - 9 + 4 + 07)^5 \\
 & := (3 + 2 - 9 + 335 - 3 + 85 + 7 + 6)^4 & := (33 - 03 + 83 - 6 + 9 + 4 + 07)^5 \\
 & := (-3 + 2 - 9 + 335 + 3 + 85 + 7 + 6)^4 & := (33 + 03 + 8 + 3 + 69 + 4 + 07)^5 \\
 & := (3 + 2 + 9 + 33 - 5 + 385 - 7 + 6)^4 & := (3 + 30 + 3 + 83 + 6 - 9 + 4 + 07)^5 \\
 & := (-3 - 2 + 9 + 33 + 5 + 385 - 7 + 6)^4 & := (3 + 30 - 3 + 83 - 6 + 9 + 4 + 07)^5 \\
 & := (-3 + 2 - 9 + 33 + 5 + 385 + 7 + 6)^4 & := (-3 + 30 + 3 + 83 - 6 + 9 + 4 + 07)^5 \\
 & := (-3 - 2 + 9 - 3 + 353 + 85 - 7 - 6)^4 & := (3 + 30 + 3 + 8 + 3 + 69 + 4 + 07)^5 \\
 & := (-3 + 2 - 9 - 3 + 353 + 85 + 7 - 6)^4 & := (3 + 3 + 038 + 3 + 69 + 4 + 07)^5 \\
 & := (3 - 2 - 9 - 3 + 353 + 85 - 7 + 6)^4 & := (33 + 038 + 36 + 9 + 4 + 07)^5 \\
 & := (-3 - 2 - 9 + 3 + 353 + 85 - 7 + 6)^4 & := (-33 - 03 + 83 + 69 + 4 + 07)^5 \\
 & := (-3 + 2 + 9 - 3 + 35 + 385 + 7 - 6)^4 & := (33 + 03 - 8 - 3 + 69 + 40 - 7)^5 \\
 & := (3 - 2 + 9 - 3 + 35 + 385 - 7 + 6)^4 & := (33 - 03 - 8 + 3 + 69 + 40 - 7)^5 \\
 & := (-3 - 2 + 9 + 3 + 35 + 385 - 7 + 6)^4 & := (3 + 30 + 38 + 36 + 9 + 4 + 07)^5 \\
 & := (3 + 2 - 9 - 3 + 35 + 385 + 7 + 6)^4 & := (-3 - 30 - 3 + 83 + 69 + 4 + 07)^5 \\
 & := (-3 + 2 - 9 + 3 + 35 + 385 + 7 + 6)^4 & := (3 + 30 + 3 - 8 - 3 + 69 + 40 - 7)^5 \\
 & := (329 + 33 - 5 - 3 + 85 - 7 - 6)^4 & := (3 + 30 - 3 - 8 + 3 + 69 + 40 - 7)^5 \\
 & := (-32 + 93 + 353 + 8 + 5 - 7 + 6)^4 & := (-3 + 30 + 3 - 8 + 3 + 69 + 40 - 7)^5
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 & := (3 - 303 + 8 - 3 + 6 + 9 + 407)^5 & := (-3 - 3 + 2 + 438 - 6 - 4 - 2 + 4 + 1)^4 \\
 & := (-3 - 303 + 8 + 3 + 6 + 9 + 407)^5 & := (-3 - 3 - 2 + 438 - 6 - 4 + 2 + 4 + 1)^4 \\
 & := (-330 + 38 - 3 + 6 + 9 + 407)^5 & := (3 + 324 + 3 + 86 + 4 + 2 + 4 + 1)^4 \\
 & := (-330 - 3 + 8 + 36 + 9 + 407)^5 & := (3 + 3 + 24 + 386 + 4 + 2 + 4 + 1)^4 \\
 & := (33 - 03 - 836 + 940 - 7)^5 & := (3 + 3 - 2 + 438 + 6 + 4 - 24 - 1)^4 \\
 & := (3 + 30 - 3 - 836 + 940 - 7)^5 & := (3 - 3 + 2 + 438 + 6 + 4 - 24 + 1)^4 \\
 & := (-3 + 30 + 3 - 836 + 940 - 7)^5 & := (-3 + 3 + 2 + 438 + 6 + 4 - 24 + 1)^4 \\
 \mathbf{33058148761} & := (33058 + 148761)^2 & := (3 + 3 + 2 - 4 + 386 + 42 - 4 - 1)^4 \\
 \mathbf{33061785241} & := (3306 + 178524 - 1)^2 & := (-3 - 3 - 2 + 4 + 386 + 42 + 4 - 1)^4 \\
 \mathbf{33138024128} & := (3313 - 80 + 2 + 4 + 1 - 28)^3 & := (3 - 3 - 2 + 4 + 386 + 42 - 4 + 1)^4 \\
 & := (3 + 3138 + 02 + 41 + 28)^3 & := (-3 + 3 - 2 + 4 + 386 + 42 - 4 + 1)^4 \\
 \mathbf{33168984597} & := (3 + 3168 + 9 + 8 + 4 + 5 + 9 + 7)^3 & := (3 - 3 - 2 - 4 + 386 + 42 + 4 + 1)^4 \\
 & := (3316 - 8 - 98 - 4 + 5 + 9 - 7)^3 & := (-3 + 3 - 2 - 4 + 386 + 42 + 4 + 1)^4 \\
 & := (3316 - 8 + 9 - 8 - 4 + 5 - 97)^3 & := (3 + 3 + 2 + 4 + 386 + 4 + 24 + 1)^4 \\
 & := (-3 + 3168 + 9 - 8 + 45 + 9 - 7)^3 & := (3 - 3 + 2 + 4 + 386 - 4 - 2 + 41)^4 \\
 & := (3 + 3168 - 9 + 8 + 45 - 9 + 7)^3 & := (-3 + 3 + 2 + 4 + 386 - 4 - 2 + 41)^4 \\
 & := (3 + 3168 + 98 - 4 - 59 + 7)^3 & := (3 - 3 + 2 - 4 + 386 + 4 - 2 + 41)^4 \\
 \mathbf{33199964344} & := (3 + 3199 + 9 - 6 + 4 - 3 + 4 + 4)^3 & := (-3 + 3 + 2 - 4 + 386 + 4 - 2 + 41)^4 \\
 & := (-3 + 3199 + 9 - 6 + 4 + 3 + 4 + 4)^3 & := (3 - 3 - 2 + 4 + 386 - 4 + 2 + 41)^4 \\
 & := (3 + 3199 - 9 + 6 + 4 + 3 + 4 + 4)^3 & := (-3 + 3 - 2 + 4 + 386 - 4 + 2 + 41)^4 \\
 & := (3319 + 9 - 9 - 64 + 3 - 44)^3 & := (3 - 3 - 2 - 4 + 386 + 4 + 2 + 41)^4 \\
 & := (3319 - 9 + 9 - 64 + 3 - 44)^3 & := (-3 + 3 - 2 - 4 + 386 + 4 + 2 + 41)^4 \\
 \mathbf{33230963375} & := (3323 - 096 + 3 - 3 - 7 - 5)^3 & := (332 - 4 + 38 + 64 + 2 - 4 - 1)^4 \\
 & := (3323 - 096 - 3 + 3 - 7 - 5)^3 & := (332 + 4 + 38 + 6 + 42 + 4 + 1)^4 \\
 & := (3 + 3230 + 9 - 6 - 33 + 7 + 5)^3 & := (332 + 4 + 38 + 6 + 4 + 2 + 41)^4 \\
 & := (-3 + 3230 + 9 - 63 + 37 + 5)^3 & := (33 - 24 - 3 - 8 + 6 + 424 - 1)^4 \\
 & := (3 + 3230 - 9 + 63 + 3 - 75)^3 & := (-33 + 24 - 3 + 8 + 6 + 424 + 1)^4 \\
 & := (-3 + 3230 + 96 - 33 - 75)^3 & := (33 - 2 - 43 + 8 + 6 + 424 + 1)^4 \\
 \mathbf{33243864241} & := (3 - 3 - 2 + 438 - 6 + 4 - 2 - 4 - 1)^4 & := (3 + 324 + 3 + 8 + 64 + 24 + 1)^4 \\
 & := (-3 + 3 - 2 + 438 - 6 + 4 - 2 - 4 - 1)^4 & := (3 + 324 + 3 + 8 + 6 + 42 + 41)^4 \\
 & := (3 - 3 + 2 + 438 - 6 - 4 + 2 - 4 - 1)^4 & := (-3 - 3 - 24 + 38 - 6 + 424 + 1)^4 \\
 & := (-3 + 3 + 2 + 438 - 6 - 4 + 2 - 4 - 1)^4 & := (-3 - 3 + 2 + 438 - 6 - 42 + 41)^4 \\
 & := (3 - 3 - 2 + 438 - 6 - 4 - 2 + 4 - 1)^4 & := (33 - 243 - 8 + 642 + 4 - 1)^4 \\
 & := (-3 + 3 - 2 + 438 - 6 - 4 - 2 + 4 - 1)^4 & := (33 + 243 - 86 - 4 + 241)^4 \\
 & := (3 + 3 - 2 + 438 - 6 - 4 - 2 - 4 + 1)^4 & \mathbf{33261981696} := (3326 + 1 - 9 - 81 - 6 - 9 - 6)^3 \\
 & := (-3 - 3 - 2 + 438 + 6 - 4 - 2 - 4 + 1)^4 & := (3 + 3261 - 9 - 8 - 16 - 9 - 6)^3 \\
 & := (-3 - 3 + 2 + 438 - 6 + 4 - 2 - 4 + 1)^4 & := (3326 + 1 - 98 - 16 + 9 - 6)^3 \\
 & := (-3 - 3 - 2 + 438 - 6 + 4 + 2 - 4 + 1)^4 & := (3326 + 1 + 9 - 8 - 16 - 96)^3
 \end{aligned}$$

34138350784 := (3413 - 83 + 5 - 07 - 84) ³	:= (-3 - 4 + 2 - 9 - 6 - 4 + 4 + 72 - 4 + 9) ⁶
34169931125 := (34 - 1 + 6 + 99 + 3112 - 5) ³	:= (-3 - 4 + 2 - 9 - 6 - 4 - 4 + 72 + 4 + 9) ⁶
:= (34 + 1 - 6 + 99 + 3112 + 5) ³	:= (34 + 29 - 6 + 4 + 4 + 7 - 2 - 4 - 9) ⁶
:= (3 + 4169 - 931 + 1 - 2 + 5) ³	:= (34 + 29 + 6 - 4 - 4 + 7 + 2 - 4 - 9) ⁶
34188010000 := (3 + 418 + 8 + 01 + 0000) ⁴	:= (34 + 29 - 6 + 4 - 4 + 7 - 2 + 4 - 9) ⁶
:= (341 + 88 + 01 + 0000) ⁴	:= (34 + 29 - 6 - 4 + 4 + 7 - 2 + 4 - 9) ⁶
:= (341 + 8 + 80 + 1 + 0000) ⁴	:= (34 + 29 + 6 - 4 - 4 - 7 - 2 - 4 + 9) ⁶
34264788992 := (3426 - 4 - 78 - 89 - 9 + 2) ³	:= (34 + 29 - 6 + 4 - 4 - 7 + 2 - 4 + 9) ⁶
:= (3426 + 4 + 7 - 88 - 99 - 2) ³	:= (34 + 29 - 6 - 4 + 4 - 7 + 2 - 4 + 9) ⁶
:= (3426 + 4 + 7 - 88 - 9 - 92) ³	:= (34 + 29 - 6 - 4 - 4 - 7 + 2 + 4 + 9) ⁶
:= (3426 + 4 + 7 - 8 - 89 - 92) ³	:= (34 - 2 + 9 - 6 + 44 - 7 - 2 - 4 - 9) ⁶
34296447249 := (34 - 2 + 9 + 6 + 4 - 4 + 7 - 2 - 4 + 9) ⁶	:= (34 + 2 - 9 - 6 + 44 + 7 - 2 - 4 - 9) ⁶
:= (34 - 2 + 9 + 6 - 4 + 4 + 7 - 2 - 4 + 9) ⁶	:= (34 - 2 - 9 - 6 + 44 + 7 + 2 - 4 - 9) ⁶
:= (34 + 2 + 9 - 6 + 4 + 4 + 7 - 2 - 4 + 9) ⁶	:= (34 - 2 - 9 - 6 + 44 - 7 - 2 - 4 + 9) ⁶
:= (34 + 2 + 9 + 6 - 4 - 4 + 7 + 2 - 4 + 9) ⁶	:= (34 - 2 - 9 + 6 - 4 + 47 - 2 - 4 - 9) ⁶
:= (34 - 2 + 9 - 6 + 4 + 4 + 7 + 2 - 4 + 9) ⁶	:= (34 + 2 - 9 - 6 + 4 + 47 - 2 - 4 - 9) ⁶
:= (34 - 2 + 9 + 6 - 4 - 4 + 7 - 2 + 4 + 9) ⁶	:= (34 - 2 - 9 - 6 + 4 + 47 + 2 - 4 - 9) ⁶
:= (34 + 2 + 9 - 6 + 4 - 4 + 7 - 2 + 4 + 9) ⁶	:= (34 - 2 - 9 - 6 - 4 + 47 - 2 + 4 - 9) ⁶
:= (34 + 2 + 9 - 6 - 4 + 4 + 7 - 2 + 4 + 9) ⁶	:= (34 - 2 - 9 - 6 - 4 + 47 + 2 + 4 - 9) ⁶
:= (34 - 2 + 9 - 6 + 4 - 4 + 7 + 2 + 4 + 9) ⁶	:= (34 - 2 + 9 - 6 + 4 - 4 + 7 + 24 - 9) ⁶
:= (34 - 2 + 9 - 6 - 4 + 4 + 7 + 2 + 4 + 9) ⁶	:= (34 - 2 + 9 - 6 - 4 + 4 + 7 + 24 - 9) ⁶
:= (-3 - 4 - 2 + 96 - 4 - 4 - 7 - 2 - 4 - 9) ⁶	:= (34 + 2 + 9 - 6 - 4 - 4 - 7 + 24 + 9) ⁶
:= (-3 + 4 + 2 + 9 - 6 - 4 - 4 + 72 - 4 - 9) ⁶	:= (34 - 2 - 9 - 6 + 4 - 4 + 7 + 24 + 9) ⁶
:= (3 + 4 + 2 - 9 + 6 - 4 - 4 + 72 - 4 - 9) ⁶	:= (34 - 2 - 9 - 6 - 4 + 4 + 7 + 24 + 9) ⁶
:= (-3 - 4 - 2 + 9 + 6 - 4 - 4 + 72 - 4 - 9) ⁶	:= (34 - 2 - 9 - 6 + 4 - 4 - 7 - 2 + 49) ⁶
:= (-3 - 4 + 2 + 9 - 6 + 4 - 4 + 72 - 4 - 9) ⁶	:= (34 - 2 - 9 - 6 - 4 + 4 - 7 - 2 + 49) ⁶
:= (3 - 4 + 2 - 9 + 6 + 4 - 4 + 72 - 4 - 9) ⁶	:= (34 + 2 - 9 - 6 - 4 - 4 - 7 + 2 + 49) ⁶
:= (-3 - 4 + 2 + 9 - 6 - 4 + 4 + 72 - 4 - 9) ⁶	:= (3 - 42 + 96 + 4 + 4 + 7 - 2 - 4 - 9) ⁶
:= (3 - 4 + 2 - 9 + 6 - 4 + 4 + 72 - 4 - 9) ⁶	:= (3 - 42 + 96 + 4 - 4 + 7 - 2 + 4 - 9) ⁶
:= (3 + 4 - 2 - 9 - 6 + 4 + 4 + 72 - 4 - 9) ⁶	:= (3 - 42 + 96 - 4 + 4 + 7 - 2 + 4 - 9) ⁶
:= (-3 - 4 + 2 + 9 - 6 - 4 - 4 + 72 + 4 - 9) ⁶	:= (3 - 42 + 96 + 4 - 4 - 7 + 2 - 4 + 9) ⁶
:= (3 - 4 + 2 - 9 + 6 - 4 - 4 + 72 + 4 - 9) ⁶	:= (3 - 42 + 96 - 4 + 4 - 7 + 2 - 4 + 9) ⁶
:= (3 + 4 - 2 - 9 - 6 + 4 - 4 + 72 + 4 - 9) ⁶	:= (-3 - 42 + 96 - 4 - 4 + 7 + 2 - 4 + 9) ⁶
:= (3 + 4 - 2 - 9 - 6 - 4 + 4 + 72 + 4 - 9) ⁶	:= (3 - 42 + 96 - 4 - 4 - 7 + 2 + 4 + 9) ⁶
:= (3 - 4 - 2 - 9 - 6 + 4 + 4 + 72 + 4 - 9) ⁶	:= (3 - 42 + 9 - 6 + 4 + 4 + 72 + 4 + 9) ⁶
:= (-3 + 4 + 2 - 9 - 6 - 4 - 4 + 72 - 4 + 9) ⁶	:= (3 + 4 - 29 - 6 + 4 + 4 + 72 - 4 + 9) ⁶
:= (-3 - 4 - 2 - 9 + 6 - 4 - 4 + 72 - 4 + 9) ⁶	:= (3 + 4 - 29 - 6 + 4 - 4 + 72 + 4 + 9) ⁶
:= (-3 - 4 + 2 - 9 - 6 + 4 - 4 + 72 - 4 + 9) ⁶	:= (3 + 4 - 29 - 6 - 4 + 4 + 72 + 4 + 9) ⁶

$$\begin{aligned} &:= (3 - 4 - 29 - 6 + 4 + 4 + 72 + 4 + 9)^6 && := (34 - 29 - 6 - 4 + 4 + 7 + 2 + 49)^6 \\ &:= (3 + 4 + 2 + 96 - 44 + 7 + 2 - 4 - 9)^6 && := (34 + 2 + 96 - 4 - 4 - 72 - 4 + 9)^6 \\ &:= (3 + 4 - 2 + 96 - 44 + 7 - 2 + 4 - 9)^6 && := (34 - 2 - 9 + 64 - 4 + 7 - 24 - 9)^6 \\ &:= (3 - 4 + 2 + 96 - 44 + 7 + 2 + 4 - 9)^6 && := (34 - 2 + 9 + 64 - 4 + 7 - 2 - 49)^6 \\ &:= (3 + 4 + 2 + 96 - 44 - 7 - 2 - 4 + 9)^6 && := (34 + 2 + 9 - 6 + 44 + 7 - 24 - 9)^6 \\ &:= (-3 - 4 + 2 + 96 - 44 + 7 - 2 - 4 + 9)^6 && := (34 - 2 + 9 - 6 + 44 - 7 - 24 + 9)^6 \\ &:= (3 + 4 - 2 + 96 - 44 - 7 + 2 - 4 + 9)^6 && := (34 + 2 - 9 - 6 + 44 + 7 - 24 + 9)^6 \\ &:= (-3 - 4 - 2 + 96 - 44 + 7 + 2 - 4 + 9)^6 && := (34 - 2 + 9 + 6 - 44 + 7 - 2 + 49)^6 \\ &:= (3 - 4 + 2 + 96 - 44 - 7 - 2 + 4 + 9)^6 && := (34 - 2 + 9 + 6 - 4 + 47 - 24 - 9)^6 \\ &:= (3 - 4 - 2 + 96 - 44 - 7 + 2 + 4 + 9)^6 && := (34 + 2 + 9 - 6 + 4 + 47 - 24 - 9)^6 \\ &:= (3 + 4 + 2 + 96 - 4 - 47 - 2 - 4 + 9)^6 && := (34 - 2 - 9 + 6 - 4 + 47 - 24 + 9)^6 \\ &:= (3 - 4 + 2 + 96 + 4 - 47 - 2 - 4 + 9)^6 && := (34 + 2 - 9 - 6 + 4 + 47 - 24 + 9)^6 \\ &:= (3 + 4 - 2 + 96 - 4 - 47 + 2 - 4 + 9)^6 && := (-34 - 2 + 9 - 6 - 4 + 47 - 2 + 49)^6 \\ &:= (3 - 4 - 2 + 96 + 4 - 47 + 2 - 4 + 9)^6 && := (3 - 42 + 96 - 4 - 4 - 7 + 24 - 9)^6 \\ &:= (3 - 4 + 2 + 96 - 4 - 47 - 2 + 4 + 9)^6 && := (3 - 42 + 96 + 4 + 4 + 7 - 24 + 9)^6 \\ &:= (3 - 4 - 2 + 96 - 4 - 47 + 2 + 4 + 9)^6 && := (-3 + 42 + 9 - 64 - 4 + 72 - 4 + 9)^6 \\ &:= (3 + 4 + 2 + 96 - 4 - 4 - 7 - 24 - 9)^6 && := (-3 + 42 + 9 + 64 + 4 - 72 + 4 + 9)^6 \\ &:= (3 - 4 + 2 + 96 + 4 - 4 - 7 - 24 - 9)^6 && := (-3 + 42 + 9 - 6 - 44 + 72 - 4 - 9)^6 \\ &:= (3 - 4 + 2 + 96 - 4 + 4 - 7 - 24 - 9)^6 && := (3 + 42 - 9 + 6 - 44 + 72 - 4 - 9)^6 \\ &:= (-3 - 4 + 2 + 96 - 4 - 4 + 7 - 24 - 9)^6 && := (3 - 42 - 9 - 6 + 44 + 72 + 4 - 9)^6 \\ &:= (-3 - 4 - 2 + 96 - 4 - 4 - 7 - 24 + 9)^6 && := (-3 + 42 - 9 - 6 - 44 + 72 - 4 + 9)^6 \\ &:= (3 + 4 - 2 + 96 + 4 - 4 + 7 - 2 - 49)^6 && := (-3 + 42 + 9 - 6 - 4 - 4 + 72 - 49)^6 \\ &:= (3 + 4 - 2 + 96 - 4 + 4 + 7 - 2 - 49)^6 && := (3 + 42 - 9 + 6 - 4 - 4 + 72 - 49)^6 \\ &:= (3 - 4 - 2 + 96 + 4 + 4 + 7 - 2 - 49)^6 && := (3 + 4 + 29 + 6 - 44 + 72 - 4 - 9)^6 \\ &:= (3 + 4 + 2 + 96 - 4 - 4 + 7 + 2 - 49)^6 && := (3 - 4 + 29 + 6 - 44 + 72 + 4 - 9)^6 \\ &:= (3 - 4 + 2 + 96 + 4 - 4 + 7 + 2 - 49)^6 && := (-3 + 4 + 29 - 6 - 44 + 72 - 4 + 9)^6 \\ &:= (3 - 4 + 2 + 96 - 4 + 4 + 7 + 2 - 49)^6 && := (-3 - 4 + 29 - 6 - 44 + 72 + 4 + 9)^6 \\ &:= (3 + 4 + 2 + 9 + 6 - 44 + 72 - 4 + 9)^6 && := (3 + 4 + 29 + 6 - 4 - 4 + 72 - 49)^6 \\ &:= (3 - 4 + 2 + 9 + 6 - 44 + 72 + 4 + 9)^6 && := (3 - 4 + 29 + 6 + 4 - 4 + 72 - 49)^6 \\ &:= (34 - 29 + 64 - 4 + 7 - 2 - 4 - 9)^6 && := (3 - 4 + 29 + 6 - 4 + 4 + 72 - 49)^6 \\ &:= (34 - 29 - 6 + 44 + 7 + 2 - 4 + 9)^6 && := (3 - 4 - 2 + 96 - 44 - 7 + 24 - 9)^6 \\ &:= (34 - 29 + 6 - 4 + 47 - 2 - 4 + 9)^6 && := (3 - 4 - 2 + 96 - 4 - 47 + 24 - 9)^6 \\ &:= (34 - 29 - 6 + 4 + 47 + 2 - 4 + 9)^6 && := (-3 + 4 + 2 + 9 + 64 + 4 - 72 + 49)^6 \\ &:= (34 - 29 - 6 - 4 + 47 + 2 + 4 + 9)^6 && := (-3 - 4 + 2 + 9 - 64 - 4 + 72 + 49)^6 \\ &:= (34 + 29 - 6 - 4 - 4 - 7 + 24 - 9)^6 && := (3 + 4 - 2 - 9 - 64 + 4 + 72 + 49)^6 \\ &:= (34 + 29 - 6 + 4 + 4 + 7 - 24 + 9)^6 && := (3 + 4 - 2 - 9 - 6 + 44 + 72 - 49)^6 \\ &:= (34 - 29 + 6 - 4 - 4 + 7 - 2 + 49)^6 && := (-3 - 4 + 2 - 9 - 6 - 44 + 72 + 49)^6 \\ &:= (34 - 29 - 6 + 4 - 4 + 7 + 2 + 49)^6 && := (34 + 29 - 64 + 47 - 2 + 4 + 9)^6 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 &:= (34 - 29 + 64 - 4 + 7 - 24 + 9)^6 && := (34 - 3 + 5 + 9 - 7 - 3 + 8 + 3 - 6 - 8)^7 \\
 &:= (34 + 29 - 64 + 4 + 7 - 2 + 49)^6 && := (34 + 3 - 5 + 9 + 7 - 3 - 8 - 3 + 6 - 8)^7 \\
 &:= (34 + 29 - 6 + 44 + 7 - 2 - 49)^6 && := (34 - 3 - 5 + 9 + 7 + 3 - 8 - 3 + 6 - 8)^7 \\
 &:= (34 + 29 - 6 - 44 - 7 + 2 + 49)^6 && := (34 + 3 + 5 - 9 - 7 + 3 + 8 - 3 + 6 - 8)^7 \\
 &:= (34 - 29 - 6 - 4 + 47 + 24 - 9)^6 && := (34 - 3 - 5 + 9 + 7 - 3 - 8 + 3 + 6 - 8)^7 \\
 &:= (34 + 29 - 6 + 4 + 47 - 2 - 49)^6 && := (34 + 3 + 5 - 9 - 7 - 3 + 8 + 3 + 6 - 8)^7 \\
 &:= (34 + 29 - 6 - 4 - 47 + 2 + 49)^6 && := (34 - 3 + 5 - 9 - 7 + 3 + 8 + 3 + 6 - 8)^7 \\
 &:= (34 - 2 - 96 + 44 + 72 - 4 + 9)^6 && := (-34 + 3 + 5 + 9 + 7 + 3 + 8 + 3 + 6 - 8)^{35} \\
 &:= (34 - 2 - 96 + 4 - 4 + 72 + 49)^6 && := (34 + 3 + 5 + 9 - 7 - 3 - 8 - 3 - 6 + 8)^7 \\
 &:= (34 - 2 - 96 - 4 + 4 + 72 + 49)^6 && := (34 - 3 + 5 + 9 - 7 + 3 - 8 - 3 - 6 + 8)^7 \\
 &:= (34 - 2 + 9 - 64 + 47 + 24 + 9)^6 && := (34 - 3 - 5 + 9 - 7 - 3 + 8 - 3 - 6 + 8)^7 \\
 &:= (34 + 2 - 9 - 64 + 47 - 2 + 49)^6 && := (34 - 3 + 5 + 9 - 7 - 3 - 8 + 3 - 6 + 8)^7 \\
 &:= (34 - 2 - 9 - 64 + 47 + 2 + 49)^6 && := (34 + 3 - 5 - 9 - 7 + 3 + 8 + 3 - 6 + 8)^7 \\
 &:= (3 - 429 - 6 + 4 + 472 + 4 + 9)^6 && := (34 + 3 + 5 - 9 - 7 + 3 - 8 - 3 + 6 + 8)^7 \\
 &:= (3 + 42 + 96 - 44 - 7 - 24 - 9)^6 && := (34 + 3 - 5 - 9 - 7 - 3 + 8 - 3 + 6 + 8)^7 \\
 &:= (3 - 42 + 96 + 44 + 7 - 2 - 49)^6 && := (34 - 3 - 5 - 9 - 7 + 3 + 8 - 3 + 6 + 8)^7 \\
 &:= (3 + 42 + 96 - 44 + 7 + 2 - 49)^6 && := (-34 + 3 - 5 + 9 + 7 + 3 + 8 - 3 + 6 + 8)^{35} \\
 &:= (3 - 42 + 96 - 44 - 7 + 2 + 49)^6 && := (34 + 3 + 5 - 9 - 7 - 3 - 8 + 3 + 6 + 8)^7 \\
 &:= (3 + 42 + 96 - 4 - 47 - 24 - 9)^6 && := (34 - 3 + 5 - 9 - 7 + 3 - 8 + 3 + 6 + 8)^7 \\
 &:= (3 - 42 + 96 + 4 + 47 - 2 - 49)^6 && := (-34 + 3 + 5 + 9 + 7 + 3 - 8 + 3 + 6 + 8)^{35} \\
 &:= (3 - 42 + 96 - 4 - 47 + 2 + 49)^6 && := (34 - 3 - 5 - 9 - 7 - 3 + 8 + 3 + 6 + 8)^7 \\
 &:= (-3 + 42 - 9 + 6 + 44 - 72 + 49)^6 && := (-34 + 3 - 5 + 9 + 7 - 3 + 8 + 3 + 6 + 8)^{35} \\
 &:= (-3 + 4 + 29 + 6 + 44 - 72 + 49)^6 && := (-34 - 3 - 5 + 9 + 7 + 3 + 8 + 3 + 6 + 8)^{35} \\
 &:= (-3 - 4 + 2 - 9 - 644 + 724 - 9)^6 && := (-3 - 4 + 35 + 9 - 7 - 3 - 8 - 3 - 6 - 8)^{35} \\
 &:= (-342 - 9 - 6 + 447 - 24 - 9)^6 && := (3 + 4 + 35 + 9 - 7 - 3 + 8 - 3 - 6 - 8)^7 \\
 &:= (-342 + 9 - 6 + 447 - 2 - 49)^6 && := (-3 - 4 + 35 + 9 + 7 - 3 + 8 - 3 - 6 - 8)^7 \\
 &:= (342 + 9 + 6 - 44 - 7 - 249)^6 && := (-3 + 4 + 35 + 9 - 7 + 3 + 8 - 3 - 6 - 8)^7 \\
 &:= (342 + 9 + 6 - 4 - 47 - 249)^6 && := (3 - 4 + 35 - 9 - 7 + 3 - 8 + 3 - 6 - 8)^{35} \\
 &:= (-3 - 42 - 96 - 44 - 7 + 249)^6 && := (-3 + 4 + 35 + 9 - 7 - 3 + 8 + 3 - 6 - 8)^7 \\
 &:= (-3 - 42 - 96 - 4 - 47 + 249)^6 && := (3 - 4 + 35 - 9 + 7 + 3 + 8 + 3 - 6 - 8)^7 \\
 &:= (-3 - 42 - 96 + 447 - 249)^6 && := (3 - 4 + 35 - 9 - 7 - 3 - 8 - 3 + 6 - 8)^{35} \\
 \mathbf{34328125000} &:= (-34 + 3281 - 2 + 5 + 000)^3 && := (-3 - 4 + 35 - 9 - 7 + 3 - 8 - 3 + 6 - 8)^{35} \\
 \mathbf{34359738368} &:= (34 + 3 - 5 - 9 + 7 - 3 - 8 - 3 - 6 - 8)^{35} && := (3 - 4 + 35 - 9 + 7 - 3 + 8 - 3 + 6 - 8)^7 \\
 &:= (34 - 3 - 5 - 9 + 7 + 3 - 8 - 3 - 6 - 8)^{35} && := (3 + 4 + 35 - 9 - 7 + 3 + 8 - 3 + 6 - 8)^7 \\
 &:= (34 + 3 + 5 + 9 - 7 - 3 + 8 - 3 - 6 - 8)^7 && := (-3 - 4 + 35 - 9 + 7 + 3 + 8 - 3 + 6 - 8)^7 \\
 &:= (34 - 3 + 5 + 9 - 7 + 3 + 8 - 3 - 6 - 8)^7 && := (-3 - 4 + 35 - 9 - 7 - 3 - 8 + 3 + 6 - 8)^{35} \\
 &:= (34 - 3 - 5 - 9 + 7 - 3 - 8 + 3 - 6 - 8)^{35} && := (3 - 4 + 35 + 9 - 7 + 3 - 8 + 3 + 6 - 8)^7 \\
 &:= (34 + 3 - 5 + 9 + 7 + 3 - 8 + 3 - 6 - 8)^7 && := (3 + 4 + 35 - 9 - 7 - 3 + 8 + 3 + 6 - 8)^7
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} & := (-3-4+35-9+7-3+8+3+6-8)^7 & := (-3-4+3-5-9-7+38+3-6-8)^{35} \\ & := (-3+4+35-9-7+3+8+3+6-8)^7 & := (-3+4-3+5+9-7+38+3-6-8)^7 \\ & := (3+4+35+9-7-3-8-3-6+8)^7 & := (3-4+3+5-9+7+38+3-6-8)^7 \\ & := (-3-4+35+9+7-3-8-3-6+8)^7 & := (-3-4-3-5-9-7+38-3+6-8)^{35} \\ & := (-3+4+35+9-7+3-8-3-6+8)^7 & := (3+4+3+5-9-7+38-3+6-8)^7 \\ & := (-3+4+35+9-7-3-8+3-6+8)^7 & := (3-4+3-5+9-7+38-3+6-8)^7 \\ & := (3-4+35-9+7+3-8+3-6+8)^7 & := (3-4-3+5-9+7+38-3+6-8)^7 \\ & := (3-4+35-9+7-3-8-3+6+8)^7 & := (-3-4+3+5-9+7+38-3+6-8)^7 \\ & := (3+4+35-9-7+3-8-3+6+8)^7 & := (3+4-3+5-9-7+38+3+6-8)^7 \\ & := (-3-4+35-9+7+3-8-3+6+8)^7 & := (-3+4+3+5-9-7+38+3+6-8)^7 \\ & := (3-4-35+9+7+3+8-3+6+8)^{35} & := (3-4-3-5+9-7+38+3+6-8)^7 \\ & := (3+4+35-9-7-3-8+3+6+8)^7 & := (-3-4+3-5+9-7+38+3+6-8)^7 \\ & := (-3-4+35-9+7-3-8+3+6+8)^7 & := (-3-4-3+5-9+7+38+3+6-8)^7 \\ & := (-3+4+35-9-7+3-8+3+6+8)^7 & := (-3+4-3-5+9-7+38-3-6+8)^7 \\ & := (3-4-35+9+7-3+8+3+6+8)^{35} & := (3-4+3-5-9+7+38-3-6+8)^7 \\ & := (3+4-35+9-7+3+8+3+6+8)^{35} & := (3+4+3-5-9-7+38+3-6+8)^7 \\ & := (-3-4-35+9+7+3+8+3+6+8)^{35} & := (3-4-3-5-9+7+38+3-6+8)^7 \\ & := (3-4+3+59-7+3-8-3-6-8)^7 & := (-3-4+3-5-9+7+38+3-6+8)^7 \\ & := (3-4+3+59-7-3-8+3-6-8)^7 & := (3+4-3-5-9-7+38-3+6+8)^7 \\ & := (3-4-3+59-7+3-8+3-6-8)^7 & := (-3+4+3-5-9-7+38-3+6+8)^7 \\ & := (-3-4+3+59-7+3-8+3-6-8)^7 & := (-3-4-3-5-9+7+38-3+6+8)^7 \\ & := (3-4-3+59-7-3-8-3+6-8)^7 & := (3-4+3+5+9+7-38+3+6+8)^{35} \\ & := (-3-4+3+59-7-3-8-3+6-8)^7 & := (-3+4-3-5-9-7+38+3+6+8)^7 \\ & := (-3-4-3+59-7+3-8-3+6-8)^7 & := (3-4-3+5-9-7-3-8+36-8)^{35} \\ & := (-3-4-3+59-7-3-8+3+6-8)^7 & := (-3-4+3+5-9-7-3-8+36-8)^{35} \\ & := (3+4+3+5+97+3+8+3-6+8)^5 & := (3+4-3-5+9+7-3-8+36-8)^7 \\ & := (3+4+3+5+97-3+8-3+6+8)^5 & := (-3+4+3-5+9+7-3-8+36-8)^7 \\ & := (3+4-3+5+97+3+8-3+6+8)^5 & := (-3-4-3+5-9-7+3-8+36-8)^{35} \\ & := (-3+4+3+5+97+3+8-3+6+8)^5 & := (3-4+3+5+9-7+3-8+36-8)^7 \\ & := (3+4-3+5+97-3+8+3+6+8)^5 & := (-3+4-3-5+9+7+3-8+36-8)^7 \\ & := (-3+4+3+5+97-3+8+3+6+8)^5 & := (-3-4-3-5-9-7-3+8+36-8)^{35} \\ & := (-3+4-3+5+97+3+8+3+6+8)^5 & := (3+4+3+5-9-7-3+8+36-8)^7 \\ & := (-3+4-3-5-9+73-8-3-6-8)^7 & := (3-4+3-5+9-7-3+8+36-8)^7 \\ & := (3-4+3-5-9-7+38-3-6-8)^{35} & := (3-4-3+5-9+7-3+8+36-8)^7 \\ & := (3+4-3+5+9-7+38-3-6-8)^7 & := (-3-4+3+5-9+7-3+8+36-8)^7 \\ & := (-3+4+3+5+9-7+38-3-6-8)^7 & := (3+4-3+5-9-7+3+8+36-8)^7 \\ & := (-3-4-3+5+9+7+38-3-6-8)^7 & := (-3+4+3+5-9-7+3+8+36-8)^7 \\ & := (3-4-3-5-9-7+38+3-6-8)^{35} & := (3-4-3-5+9-7+3+8+36-8)^7 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} & := (-3-4+3-5+9-7+3+8+36-8)^7 & := (-34-3+5-9+7+3-8+3+68)^7 \\ & := (-3-4-3+5-9+7+3+8+36-8)^7 & := (-34-3-5-9+7-3+8+3+68)^7 \\ & := (3+4-3+5+9+7-3+8-36+8)^{35} & := (34-3+5+9+7-3+8+3+68)^5 \\ & := (-3+4+3+5+9+7-3+8-36+8)^{35} & := (3-43+59-7+3-8-3+6-8)^{35} \\ & := (-3+4-3+5+9+7+3+8-36+8)^{35} & := (3-43+59+7+3+8-3+6-8)^7 \\ & := (-3-4-3-5-9-7-3-8+36+8)^{35} & := (3-43+59-7-3-8+3+6-8)^{35} \\ & := (3+4+3+5-9-7-3-8+36+8)^7 & := (-3-43+59-7+3-8+3+6-8)^{35} \\ & := (3-4+3-5+9-7-3-8+36+8)^7 & := (3-43+59+7-3+8+3+6-8)^7 \\ & := (3-4-3+5-9+7-3-8+36+8)^7 & := (-3-43+59+7+3+8+3+6-8)^7 \\ & := (-3-4+3+5-9+7-3-8+36+8)^7 & := (3+43+59+7+3+8+3-6+8)^5 \\ & := (3+4-3+5-9-7+3-8+36+8)^7 & := (3-43+59+7+3-8-3+6+8)^7 \\ & := (-3+4+3+5-9-7+3-8+36+8)^7 & := (3+43+59+7-3+8-3+6+8)^5 \\ & := (3-4-3-5+9-7+3-8+36+8)^7 & := (3+43-59-7+3+8-3+6+8)^{35} \\ & := (-3-4+3-5+9-7+3-8+36+8)^7 & := (-3+43+59+7+3+8-3+6+8)^5 \\ & := (-3-4-3+5-9+7+3-8+36+8)^7 & := (3-43+59+7-3-8+3+6+8)^7 \\ & := (3+4-3-5-9-7-3+8+36+8)^7 & := (-3-43+59+7+3-8+3+6+8)^7 \\ & := (-3+4+3-5-9-7-3+8+36+8)^7 & := (3+43-59-7-3+8+3+6+8)^{35} \\ & := (-3-4-3-5-9+7-3+8+36+8)^7 & := (-3+43+59+7-3+8+3+6+8)^5 \\ & := (-3+4-3-5-9-7+3+8+36+8)^7 & := (-3+43-59-7+3+8+3+6+8)^{35} \\ & := (-34+3-5+9-7-3+83-6-8)^7 & := (3+43-5+97+3-8-3+6-8)^5 \\ & := (-34-3+5-9+7-3+83-6-8)^7 & := (3+43-5+97-3-8+3+6-8)^5 \\ & := (-34-3-5+9-7+3+83-6-8)^7 & := (-3+43-5+97+3-8+3+6-8)^5 \\ & := (-34+3-5-9-7+3+83+6-8)^7 & := (-3-43+5+9+73+8-3-6-8)^7 \\ & := (34+3+5+9-7+3+83+6-8)^5 & := (3-43+5-9+73+8-3+6-8)^7 \\ & := (34+3+5-9+7+3+83-6+8)^5 & := (-3-43+5-9+73+8+3+6-8)^7 \\ & := (34+3-5+9-7-3+83+6+8)^5 & := (-3-43+5+9+73-8-3-6+8)^7 \\ & := (34-3+5-9+7-3+83+6+8)^5 & := (3-43-5-9+73+8+3-6+8)^7 \\ & := (34-3-5+9-7+3+83+6+8)^5 & := (3+43+5-9+73+8+3-6+8)^5 \\ & := (-34+3-5-9-7-3-8-3+68)^{35} & := (3-43+5-9+73-8-3+6+8)^7 \\ & := (-34-3-5-9-7+3-8-3+68)^{35} & := (-3-43-5-9+73+8-3+6+8)^7 \\ & := (-34+3+5-9+7+3-8-3+68)^7 & := (-3+43+5-9+73+8-3+6+8)^5 \\ & := (-34+3-5-9+7-3+8-3+68)^7 & := (-3-43+5-9+73-8+3+6+8)^7 \\ & := (34+3+5+9+7-3+8-3+68)^5 & := (3+43-5+9-73+8+3+6+8)^{35} \\ & := (-34-3-5-9+7+3+8-3+68)^7 & := (3+43-5+9+7-38-3-6-8)^{35} \\ & := (34-3+5+9+7+3+8-3+68)^5 & := (3-43+5+9+7+38-3-6-8)^{35} \\ & := (-34-3-5-9-7-3-8+3+68)^{35} & := (-3+43-5+9+7-38+3-6-8)^{35} \\ & := (-34+3+5-9+7-3-8+3+68)^7 & := (-3-43+5+9+7+38+3-6-8)^{35} \\ & := (-34+3-5+9-7+3-8+3+68)^7 & := (3+43-5-9+7-38+3+6-8)^{35} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} &:= (3 - 43 + 5 - 9 + 7 + 38 + 3 + 6 - 8)^{35} &:= (-3 + 4 + 35 + 9 + 7 - 3 + 8 + 3 + 68)^5 \\ &:= (-3 - 43 - 5 + 9 + 7 + 38 - 3 - 6 + 8)^{35} &:= (-3 + 4 - 35 - 9 - 7 + 3 + 8 + 3 + 68)^7 \\ &:= (3 + 43 + 5 - 9 - 7 - 38 + 3 - 6 + 8)^{35} &:= (3 - 4 + 3 - 59 - 7 - 3 + 83 - 6 - 8)^{35} \\ &:= (-3 + 43 + 5 - 9 - 7 - 38 - 3 + 6 + 8)^{35} &:= (3 + 4 + 3 + 59 - 7 - 3 + 83 - 6 - 8)^5 \\ &:= (3 - 43 - 5 - 9 + 7 + 38 - 3 + 6 + 8)^{35} &:= (3 - 4 - 3 + 59 + 7 - 3 + 83 - 6 - 8)^5 \\ &:= (3 + 43 + 5 + 9 - 7 - 38 + 3 + 6 + 8)^7 &:= (-3 - 4 + 3 + 59 + 7 - 3 + 83 - 6 - 8)^5 \\ &:= (-3 - 43 - 5 - 9 + 7 + 38 + 3 + 6 + 8)^{35} &:= (3 - 4 - 3 - 59 - 7 + 3 + 83 - 6 - 8)^{35} \\ &:= (3 + 43 - 5 + 9 + 7 - 3 - 8 - 36 - 8)^{35} &:= (-3 - 4 + 3 - 59 - 7 + 3 + 83 - 6 - 8)^{35} \\ &:= (-3 + 43 - 5 + 9 + 7 + 3 - 8 - 36 - 8)^{35} &:= (3 + 4 - 3 + 59 - 7 + 3 + 83 - 6 - 8)^5 \\ &:= (3 + 43 + 5 - 9 - 7 + 3 + 8 - 36 - 8)^{35} &:= (-3 + 4 + 3 + 59 - 7 + 3 + 83 - 6 - 8)^5 \\ &:= (3 - 43 + 5 - 9 + 7 + 3 + 8 + 36 - 8)^{35} &:= (-3 - 4 - 3 + 59 + 7 + 3 + 83 - 6 - 8)^5 \\ &:= (3 + 43 + 5 - 9 - 7 + 3 - 8 - 36 + 8)^{35} &:= (-3 - 4 - 3 - 59 - 7 - 3 + 83 + 6 - 8)^{35} \\ &:= (3 + 43 - 5 - 9 - 7 - 3 + 8 - 36 + 8)^{35} &:= (-3 + 4 - 3 + 59 - 7 - 3 + 83 + 6 - 8)^5 \\ &:= (-3 + 43 - 5 - 9 - 7 + 3 + 8 - 36 + 8)^{35} &:= (3 - 4 + 3 - 59 + 7 - 3 + 83 - 6 + 8)^7 \\ &:= (3 + 43 + 5 - 9 + 7 + 3 + 8 - 36 + 8)^7 &:= (3 + 4 + 3 - 59 - 7 + 3 + 83 - 6 + 8)^7 \\ &:= (3 - 43 + 5 - 9 + 7 + 3 - 8 + 36 + 8)^{35} &:= (3 - 4 - 3 - 59 + 7 + 3 + 83 - 6 + 8)^7 \\ &:= (3 - 43 - 5 - 9 + 7 - 3 + 8 + 36 + 8)^{35} &:= (-3 - 4 + 3 - 59 + 7 + 3 + 83 - 6 + 8)^7 \\ &:= (-3 - 43 - 5 - 9 + 7 + 3 + 8 + 36 + 8)^{35} &:= (3 - 4 + 3 + 59 + 7 + 3 - 83 + 6 + 8)^{35} \\ &:= (3 - 4 - 35 + 9 - 7 - 3 + 83 - 6 - 8)^7 &:= (3 + 4 - 3 - 59 - 7 - 3 + 83 + 6 + 8)^7 \\ &:= (-3 - 4 - 35 + 9 - 7 + 3 + 83 - 6 - 8)^7 &:= (-3 + 4 + 3 - 59 - 7 - 3 + 83 + 6 + 8)^7 \\ &:= (3 - 4 + 35 + 9 + 7 - 3 + 83 + 6 - 8)^5 &:= (-3 - 4 - 3 - 59 + 7 - 3 + 83 + 6 + 8)^7 \\ &:= (3 - 4 - 35 - 9 - 7 + 3 + 83 + 6 - 8)^7 &:= (-3 + 4 - 3 - 59 - 7 + 3 + 83 + 6 + 8)^7 \\ &:= (3 + 4 + 35 + 9 - 7 + 3 + 83 + 6 - 8)^5 &:= (3 - 4 + 3 + 59 + 7 - 3 + 8 - 3 - 68)^{35} \\ &:= (-3 - 4 + 35 + 9 + 7 + 3 + 83 + 6 - 8)^5 &:= (3 + 4 + 3 + 59 - 7 + 3 + 8 - 3 - 68)^{35} \\ &:= (-3 + 4 - 35 - 9 - 7 - 3 + 83 - 6 + 8)^7 &:= (3 - 4 - 3 + 59 + 7 + 3 + 8 - 3 - 68)^{35} \\ &:= (3 + 4 + 35 - 9 + 7 + 3 + 83 - 6 + 8)^5 &:= (-3 - 4 + 3 + 59 + 7 + 3 + 8 - 3 - 68)^{35} \\ &:= (-3 + 4 + 35 - 9 + 7 - 3 + 83 + 6 + 8)^5 &:= (3 + 4 + 3 + 59 - 7 - 3 + 8 + 3 - 68)^{35} \\ &:= (3 - 4 - 35 - 9 - 7 - 3 - 8 - 3 + 68)^{35} &:= (3 - 4 - 3 + 59 + 7 - 3 + 8 + 3 - 68)^{35} \\ &:= (-3 - 4 - 35 - 9 - 7 + 3 - 8 - 3 + 68)^{35} &:= (-3 - 4 + 3 + 59 + 7 - 3 + 8 + 3 - 68)^{35} \\ &:= (3 - 4 - 35 - 9 + 7 - 3 + 8 - 3 + 68)^7 &:= (3 + 4 - 3 + 59 - 7 + 3 + 8 + 3 - 68)^{35} \\ &:= (3 + 4 + 35 + 9 + 7 - 3 + 8 - 3 + 68)^5 &:= (-3 + 4 + 3 + 59 - 7 + 3 + 8 + 3 - 68)^{35} \\ &:= (3 + 4 - 35 - 9 - 7 + 3 + 8 - 3 + 68)^7 &:= (-3 - 4 - 3 + 59 + 7 + 3 + 8 + 3 - 68)^{35} \\ &:= (-3 - 4 - 35 - 9 + 7 + 3 + 8 - 3 + 68)^7 &:= (3 - 4 + 3 + 59 + 7 + 3 - 8 - 3 + 68)^5 \\ &:= (-3 + 4 + 35 + 9 + 7 + 3 + 8 - 3 + 68)^5 &:= (-3 + 4 - 3 - 59 - 7 - 3 + 8 - 3 + 68)^{35} \\ &:= (-3 - 4 - 35 - 9 - 7 - 3 - 8 + 3 + 68)^{35} &:= (3 - 4 + 3 + 59 + 7 - 3 - 8 + 3 + 68)^5 \\ &:= (3 - 4 - 35 + 9 - 7 + 3 - 8 + 3 + 68)^7 &:= (3 - 4 + 3 - 59 - 7 + 3 - 8 + 3 + 68)^{35} \\ &:= (3 + 4 - 35 - 9 - 7 - 3 + 8 + 3 + 68)^7 &:= (3 + 4 + 3 + 59 - 7 + 3 - 8 + 3 + 68)^5 \\ &:= (-3 - 4 - 35 - 9 + 7 - 3 + 8 + 3 + 68)^7 &:= (3 - 4 - 3 + 59 + 7 + 3 - 8 + 3 + 68)^5 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} & := (-3-4+3+59+7+3-8+3+68)^5 \\ & := (3-4+3-59+7+3+8+3+68)^7 \\ & := (3+4+3-5+97-3-83-6-8)^{35} \\ & := (3+4-3-5+97+3-83-6-8)^{35} \\ & := (-3+4+3-5+97+3-83-6-8)^{35} \\ & := (-3+4-3-5+97-3-83+6-8)^{35} \\ & := (3+4+3+5-97+3+83+6-8)^{35} \\ & := (3-4+3+5+97-3-83+6+8)^7 \\ & := (3-4-3+5+97+3-83+6+8)^7 \\ & := (-3-4+3+5+97+3-83+6+8)^7 \\ & := (3+4+3-5-97-3+83+6+8)^{35} \\ & := (3+4-3-5-97+3+83+6+8)^{35} \\ & := (-3+4+3-5-97+3+83+6+8)^{35} \\ & := (3-4-3+5+97-3+8-3-68)^7 \\ & := (-3-4+3+5+97-3+8-3-68)^7 \\ & := (-3-4-3+5+97+3+8-3-68)^7 \\ & := (3+4+3-5+97+3-8+3-68)^7 \\ & := (-3-4-3+5+97-3+8+3-68)^7 \\ & := (3+4+3+5-9-73+83-6-8)^{35} \\ & := (3-4+3-5+9-73+83-6-8)^{35} \\ & := (-3-4-3+5-9+73+83-6-8)^5 \\ & := (3+4+3-5+9+73-83+6-8)^{35} \\ & := (-3+4-3+5-9-73+83+6-8)^{35} \\ & := (-3-4-3-5+9-73+83+6-8)^{35} \\ & := (3+4+3+5+9-73+83+6-8)^7 \\ & := (3-4-3+5+9+73-83-6+8)^{35} \\ & := (-3-4+3+5+9+73-83-6+8)^{35} \\ & := (3+4-3-5-9-73+83-6+8)^{35} \\ & := (-3+4+3-5-9-73+83-6+8)^{35} \\ & := (3-4+3+5-9+73-83+6+8)^{35} \\ & := (3+4-3-5+9-73+83+6+8)^7 \\ & := (-3+4+3-5+9-73+83+6+8)^7 \\ & := (3+4-3-5+9+73-8-3-68)^{35} \\ & := (-3+4+3-5+9+73-8-3-68)^{35} \\ & := (3-4-3+5-9+73+8-3-68)^{35} \\ & := (-3+4-3-5+9+73-8+3-68)^{35} \\ & := (-3-4-3+5-9+73+8+3-68)^{35} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} & := (3-4+3+5+9+73+8+3-68)^7 \\ & := (3+4-3+5+9-73-8-3+68)^{35} \\ & := (-3+4+3+5+9-73-8-3+68)^{35} \\ & := (3-4+3+5-9+73-8-3+68)^5 \\ & := (-3+4-3-5+9-73+8-3+68)^{35} \\ & := (3-4-3-5-9+73+8-3+68)^5 \\ & := (-3-4+3-5-9+73+8-3+68)^5 \\ & := (-3+4-3+5+9-73-8+3+68)^{35} \\ & := (3-4-3+5-9+73-8+3+68)^5 \\ & := (-3-4+3+5-9+73-8+3+68)^5 \\ & := (3+4+3-5-9-73+8+3+68)^{35} \\ & := (-3-4-3-5-9+73+8+3+68)^5 \\ & := (3-4-3-5-9-7-38-3+68)^{35} \\ & := (-3-4+3-5-9-7-38-3+68)^{35} \\ & := (-3+4-3+5+9-7-38-3+68)^7 \\ & := (3-4+3+5-9+7-38-3+68)^7 \\ & := (3+4-3+5+9+7+38-3+68)^5 \\ & := (-3+4+3+5+9+7+38-3+68)^5 \\ & := (-3-4-3-5-9-7-38+3+68)^{35} \\ & := (3+4+3+5-9-7-38+3+68)^7 \\ & := (3-4+3-5+9-7-38+3+68)^7 \\ & := (3-4-3+5-9+7-38+3+68)^7 \\ & := (-3-4+3+5-9+7-38+3+68)^7 \\ & := (-3+4-3+5+9+7+38+3+68)^5 \\ & := (-34-35+97-3+8-3-6+8)^7 \\ & := (34+35+9-73+8+3-6-8)^{35} \\ & := (-34-35-9+73+8-3-6+8)^{35} \\ & := (34+35+9-73-8+3-6+8)^{35} \\ & := (-34-35+9+73+8-3+6+8)^7 \\ & := (-34+35-9+7+38-3+6-8)^7 \\ & := (34+35+9-7-38-3-6+8)^7 \\ & := (34+35+9+7+38+3-6+8)^5 \\ & := (34-35-9-7+38-3+6+8)^7 \\ & := (34+35-9-7-38+3+6+8)^7 \\ & := (-34-35+9+7+38+3+6+8)^{35} \\ & := (34+35+9-7-3+8-36-8)^7 \\ & := (-34+35-9-7-3-8+36-8)^{35} \\ & := (34-35+9+7-3-8+36-8)^7 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} & := (-34 + 35 - 9 + 7 - 3 + 8 + 36 - 8)^7 \\ & := (34 + 35 + 9 - 7 - 3 - 8 - 36 + 8)^7 \\ & := (-34 + 35 - 9 + 7 - 3 - 8 + 36 + 8)^7 \\ & := (34 - 35 - 9 - 7 - 3 + 8 + 36 + 8)^7 \\ & := (-34 - 35 + 9 + 7 + 3 + 8 + 36 + 8)^{35} \\ & := (34 + 3 - 59 + 73 - 8 + 3 - 6 - 8)^7 \\ & := (34 - 3 - 59 + 73 - 8 - 3 + 6 - 8)^7 \\ & := (34 + 3 + 59 - 73 + 8 + 3 + 6 - 8)^7 \\ & := (-34 + 3 - 59 + 73 + 8 - 3 + 6 + 8)^{35} \\ & := (34 + 3 + 59 - 73 - 8 + 3 + 6 + 8)^7 \\ & := (-34 - 3 - 59 + 73 + 8 + 3 + 6 + 8)^{35} \\ & := (34 + 3 + 59 - 7 + 38 + 3 + 6 - 8)^5 \\ & := (34 - 3 - 59 - 7 + 38 - 3 - 6 + 8)^{35} \\ & := (-34 + 3 + 59 + 7 - 38 + 3 - 6 + 8)^{35} \\ & := (-34 - 3 + 59 + 7 - 38 - 3 + 6 + 8)^{35} \\ & := (-34 + 3 + 59 + 7 + 3 + 8 - 36 - 8)^{35} \\ & := (-34 - 3 + 59 - 7 - 3 - 8 + 36 - 8)^7 \\ & := (34 + 3 - 59 + 7 - 3 - 8 + 36 - 8)^{35} \\ & := (34 - 3 - 59 + 7 + 3 - 8 + 36 - 8)^{35} \\ & := (34 + 3 + 59 - 7 + 3 + 8 + 36 - 8)^5 \\ & := (-34 + 3 + 59 + 7 + 3 - 8 - 36 + 8)^{35} \\ & := (34 + 3 + 59 - 7 + 3 - 8 + 36 + 8)^5 \\ & := (-34 + 3 + 5 + 97 - 38 - 3 - 6 + 8)^7 \\ & := (-34 - 3 + 5 + 97 - 38 + 3 - 6 + 8)^7 \\ & := (-34 + 3 + 5 + 97 - 3 + 8 - 36 - 8)^7 \\ & := (-34 - 3 + 5 + 97 + 3 + 8 - 36 - 8)^7 \\ & := (-34 + 3 + 5 + 97 - 3 - 8 - 36 + 8)^7 \\ & := (-34 - 3 + 5 + 97 + 3 - 8 - 36 + 8)^7 \\ & := (-34 - 3 - 5 + 97 - 3 + 8 - 36 + 8)^7 \\ & := (-34 + 3 + 5 - 9 + 73 + 8 - 36 - 8)^{35} \\ & := (34 - 3 - 5 + 9 + 73 - 8 + 36 - 8)^5 \\ & := (-34 + 3 + 5 - 9 + 73 - 8 - 36 + 8)^{35} \\ & := (-34 - 3 - 5 - 9 + 73 + 8 - 36 + 8)^{35} \\ & := (34 + 3 - 5 - 9 - 73 + 8 + 36 + 8)^{35} \\ & := (34 - 3 + 5 + 9 - 7 + 38 - 36 - 8)^7 \\ & := (34 - 3 - 5 + 9 + 7 - 38 + 36 - 8)^7 \\ & := (-34 + 3 - 5 + 9 - 7 + 38 + 36 - 8)^7 \\ & := (-34 - 3 + 5 - 9 + 7 + 38 + 36 - 8)^7 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} & := (34 + 3 + 5 - 9 - 7 - 38 + 36 + 8)^7 \\ & := (34 - 3 + 5 - 9 - 7 - 3 + 83 - 68)^7 \\ & := (-34 + 3 + 5 + 9 + 7 - 3 + 83 - 68)^{35} \\ & := (-34 - 3 + 5 + 9 + 7 + 3 + 83 - 68)^{35} \\ & := (34 - 3 + 5 - 9 - 7 - 3 - 83 + 68)^{35} \\ & := (34 + 3 + 5 + 9 - 7 + 3 - 83 + 68)^7 \\ & := (-34 + 3 - 5 + 9 + 7 - 3 + 83 + 68)^5 \\ & := (-34 - 3 - 5 + 9 + 7 + 3 + 83 + 68)^5 \\ & := (3 + 43 + 59 - 7 + 3 - 83 + 6 + 8)^7 \\ & := (3 - 43 - 59 + 7 - 3 + 83 + 6 + 8)^{35} \\ & := (-3 - 43 - 59 + 7 + 3 + 83 + 6 + 8)^{35} \\ & := (3 + 43 + 59 - 7 - 3 + 8 - 3 - 68)^7 \\ & := (-3 + 43 + 59 - 7 + 3 + 8 - 3 - 68)^7 \\ & := (-3 + 43 + 59 - 7 - 3 + 8 + 3 - 68)^7 \\ & := (-3 + 43 - 5 + 97 - 3 - 83 - 6 - 8)^7 \\ & := (3 - 43 + 5 + 97 - 3 + 83 - 6 - 8)^5 \\ & := (-3 - 43 + 5 + 97 + 3 + 83 - 6 - 8)^5 \\ & := (3 + 43 + 5 - 97 - 3 + 83 + 6 - 8)^7 \\ & := (-3 + 43 + 5 - 97 + 3 + 83 + 6 - 8)^7 \\ & := (-3 - 43 - 5 + 97 - 3 + 83 - 6 + 8)^5 \\ & := (3 + 43 - 5 - 97 + 3 + 83 - 6 + 8)^7 \\ & := (-3 + 43 - 5 - 97 - 3 + 83 + 6 + 8)^7 \\ & := (3 - 43 + 5 + 97 + 3 + 8 - 3 - 68)^{35} \\ & := (3 - 43 + 5 + 97 - 3 + 8 + 3 - 68)^{35} \\ & := (-3 - 43 + 5 + 97 + 3 + 8 + 3 - 68)^{35} \\ & := (-3 + 43 + 5 - 97 - 3 - 8 - 3 + 68)^{35} \\ & := (3 - 43 - 5 + 97 + 3 + 8 - 3 + 68)^5 \\ & := (3 - 43 + 5 + 97 + 3 - 8 + 3 + 68)^5 \\ & := (3 - 43 - 5 + 97 - 3 + 8 + 3 + 68)^5 \\ & := (-3 - 43 - 5 + 97 + 3 + 8 + 3 + 68)^5 \\ & := (-3 + 43 - 5 - 9 + 73 - 83 - 6 - 8)^{35} \\ & := (-3 + 43 + 5 - 9 - 73 + 83 - 6 - 8)^7 \\ & := (-3 + 43 - 5 + 9 + 73 - 83 + 6 - 8)^7 \\ & := (3 - 43 + 5 + 9 + 73 + 83 + 6 - 8)^5 \\ & := (-3 - 43 - 5 + 9 + 73 + 83 + 6 + 8)^5 \\ & := (3 + 43 - 5 - 9 + 73 - 8 + 3 - 68)^7 \\ & := (3 + 43 - 5 - 9 - 73 + 8 - 3 + 68)^7 \\ & := (3 + 43 + 5 - 9 - 73 - 8 + 3 + 68)^7 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} & := (-3 + 43 - 5 - 9 - 73 + 8 + 3 + 68)^7 \\ & := (3 + 43 + 5 - 9 - 7 + 38 - 3 - 68)^{35} \\ & := (-3 + 43 + 5 - 9 - 7 + 38 + 3 - 68)^{35} \\ & := (-3 - 43 + 5 + 9 + 7 - 38 - 3 + 68)^{35} \\ & := (3 + 43 - 5 - 9 - 7 + 38 - 3 + 68)^5 \\ & := (-3 + 43 - 5 - 9 - 7 + 38 + 3 + 68)^5 \\ & := (3 + 4 - 35 + 97 - 38 + 3 + 6 - 8)^7 \\ & := (-3 - 4 - 35 + 97 - 3 + 8 - 36 + 8)^7 \\ & := (3 + 4 - 35 + 9 + 73 - 8 - 36 - 8)^{35} \\ & := (-3 - 4 + 35 - 9 + 73 + 8 + 36 - 8)^5 \\ & := (-3 - 4 - 35 - 9 + 73 + 8 - 36 + 8)^{35} \\ & := (-3 - 4 + 35 - 9 + 73 - 8 + 36 + 8)^5 \\ & := (-3 + 4 + 35 + 9 - 7 + 38 - 36 - 8)^7 \\ & := (-3 - 4 + 35 - 9 - 7 - 38 + 36 - 8)^{35} \\ & := (3 - 4 - 35 + 9 - 7 + 38 + 36 - 8)^7 \\ & := (3 + 4 + 35 - 9 - 7 - 38 + 36 + 8)^7 \\ & := (-3 - 4 + 35 - 9 + 7 - 38 + 36 + 8)^7 \\ & := (-3 + 4 - 35 - 9 - 7 + 38 + 36 + 8)^7 \\ & := (-3 + 4 + 35 - 9 - 7 - 3 + 83 - 68)^7 \\ & := (-3 + 4 + 35 - 9 - 7 - 3 - 83 + 68)^{35} \\ & := (3 - 4 + 35 + 9 + 7 - 3 - 83 + 68)^7 \\ & := (3 + 4 + 35 + 9 - 7 + 3 - 83 + 68)^7 \\ & := (-3 - 4 + 35 + 9 + 7 + 3 - 83 + 68)^7 \\ & := (3 - 4 - 35 + 9 + 7 - 3 + 83 + 68)^5 \\ & := (3 + 4 - 35 + 9 - 7 + 3 + 83 + 68)^5 \\ & := (-3 - 4 - 35 + 9 + 7 + 3 + 83 + 68)^5 \\ & := (3 - 4 - 3 + 59 - 73 - 8 + 36 - 8)^{35} \\ & := (-3 - 4 + 3 + 59 - 73 - 8 + 36 - 8)^{35} \\ & := (-3 + 4 - 3 - 59 + 73 - 8 + 36 - 8)^7 \\ & := (3 + 4 + 3 + 59 - 73 + 8 + 36 - 8)^7 \\ & := (3 + 4 + 3 + 59 - 73 - 8 + 36 + 8)^7 \\ & := (-3 - 4 - 3 + 59 - 7 - 38 + 36 - 8)^7 \\ & := (3 - 4 + 3 - 59 - 7 + 38 + 36 - 8)^{35} \\ & := (3 + 4 + 3 + 59 - 7 + 38 + 36 - 8)^5 \\ & := (3 - 4 - 3 + 59 + 7 + 38 + 36 - 8)^5 \\ & := (-3 - 4 + 3 + 59 + 7 + 38 + 36 - 8)^5 \\ & := (3 - 4 + 3 + 59 + 7 - 38 - 36 + 8)^{35} \\ & := (3 - 4 + 3 - 59 + 7 + 38 + 36 + 8)^7 \\ & := (3 - 4 + 3 - 59 + 7 + 38 + 36 + 8)^5 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} & := (-3 + 4 - 3 + 59 - 7 - 3 - 83 + 68)^7 \\ & := (3 - 4 - 3 + 5 + 97 - 38 - 36 + 8)^7 \\ & := (-3 - 4 + 3 + 5 + 97 - 38 - 36 + 8)^7 \\ & := (34 - 35 + 97 + 3 - 83 - 6 - 8)^{35} \\ & := (-34 + 35 + 97 + 3 - 83 + 6 + 8)^7 \\ & := (34 - 35 - 97 + 3 + 83 + 6 + 8)^{35} \\ & := (-34 - 35 + 97 + 3 + 83 + 6 + 8)^5 \\ & := (-34 + 35 + 97 - 3 + 8 - 3 - 68)^7 \\ & := (34 + 35 - 97 + 3 - 8 - 3 + 68)^7 \\ & := (34 + 35 - 97 - 3 - 8 + 3 + 68)^7 \\ & := (-34 + 35 + 9 + 73 - 83 - 6 + 8)^{35} \\ & := (34 - 35 - 9 - 73 + 83 - 6 + 8)^{35} \\ & := (34 - 35 + 9 - 73 + 83 + 6 + 8)^7 \\ & := (34 - 35 + 9 + 73 - 8 - 3 - 68)^{35} \\ & := (-34 + 35 - 9 + 73 + 8 - 3 - 68)^{35} \\ & := (-34 + 35 - 9 + 73 - 8 + 3 + 68)^5 \\ & := (-34 - 35 - 9 + 7 + 38 - 3 + 68)^7 \\ & := (-34 + 35 - 9 + 7 - 38 + 3 + 68)^7 \\ & := (-34 + 3 + 59 + 73 - 83 + 6 + 8)^7 \\ & := (34 + 3 - 59 - 73 + 83 + 6 + 8)^{35} \\ & := (-34 - 3 + 59 + 73 + 8 - 3 - 68)^7 \\ & := (-34 + 3 + 59 + 7 + 38 - 3 - 68)^{35} \\ & := (-34 - 3 + 59 + 7 + 38 + 3 - 68)^{35} \\ & := (-34 - 3 + 5 + 97 + 38 - 3 - 68)^7 \\ & := (34 - 3 - 5 - 97 + 38 - 3 + 68)^7 \\ & := (-3 + 43 - 59 + 73 - 8 - 36 - 8)^{35} \\ & := (3 - 43 + 59 + 73 + 8 + 36 - 8)^5 \\ & := (3 - 43 + 59 + 73 - 8 + 36 + 8)^5 \\ & := (3 - 43 + 59 - 7 - 38 + 36 - 8)^{35} \\ & := (3 + 43 + 59 - 7 - 38 - 36 + 8)^7 \\ & := (3 - 43 + 59 + 7 - 38 + 36 + 8)^7 \\ & := (-3 - 43 + 59 + 7 - 3 + 83 - 68)^7 \\ & := (-3 - 43 + 59 + 7 - 3 - 83 + 68)^{35} \\ & := (3 + 43 - 59 - 7 - 3 + 83 + 68)^5 \\ & := (-3 + 43 - 59 - 7 + 3 + 83 + 68)^5 \\ & := (3 + 43 - 5 + 97 - 38 + 36 - 8)^5 \\ & := (3 - 43 + 5 + 97 + 38 + 36 - 8)^5 \\ & := (-3 - 43 - 5 + 97 + 38 + 36 + 8)^5 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} &:= (3 + 43 + 5 + 9 - 73 + 83 - 68)^{35} \\ &:= (3 - 43 + 5 + 9 + 73 - 83 + 68)^7 \\ &:= (3 + 43 - 5 + 9 - 73 + 83 + 68)^5 \\ &:= (3 - 4 - 359 - 7 + 383 - 6 - 8)^{35} \\ &:= (3 - 4 - 359 + 7 + 383 - 6 + 8)^7 \\ &:= (-3 + 4 - 359 - 7 + 383 + 6 + 8)^7 \\ &:= (3 - 4 + 359 + 7 - 3 + 8 - 368)^{35} \\ &:= (3 + 4 + 359 - 7 + 3 + 8 - 368)^{35} \\ &:= (-3 - 4 + 359 + 7 + 3 + 8 - 368)^{35} \\ &:= (3 + 4 - 3 - 5 + 973 - 836 - 8)^5 \\ &:= (-3 + 4 + 3 - 5 + 973 - 836 - 8)^5 \\ &:= (-343 - 59 + 7 + 383 + 6 + 8)^{35} \\ &:= (343 + 59 - 7 - 3 + 8 - 368)^7 \\ &:= (-343 + 5 + 97 + 383 - 6 - 8)^5 \\ &:= (-343 - 5 + 97 + 3 + 8 + 368)^5 \\ &:= (343 + 5 - 9 - 7 + 38 - 368)^{35} \\ &:= (-34 + 35 + 97 - 38 - 36 + 8)^7 \\ &:= (34 + 35 - 9 - 73 + 83 - 68)^{35} \\ &:= (34 - 3 + 59 - 73 + 83 - 68)^7 \\ &:= (34 - 3 + 59 - 73 - 83 + 68)^{35} \\ &:= (-34 - 3 - 59 + 73 + 83 + 68)^5 \\ &:= (-3 - 435 + 97 - 3 + 8 + 368)^7 \\ &:= (-3 - 435 - 9 + 73 + 8 + 368)^{35} \\ &:= (-3 - 4 + 359 - 73 - 83 - 68)^5 \\ &:= (-34 + 359 + 7 + 38 - 368)^{35} \\ &:= (34 - 35 + 973 - 836 - 8)^5 \\ &:= (343 + 59 - 738 + 368)^7 \end{aligned}$$

$$\mathbf{34423275277} := (-3 + 4 + 423 + 2752 + 77)^3$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{34507149121} &:= (345 + 071 + 4 + 9 + 1 + 2 - 1)^4 \\ &:= (345 + 071 + 4 + 9 - 1 + 2 + 1)^4 \\ &:= (345 - 07 + 1 + 4 + 91 - 2 - 1)^4 \\ &:= (345 - 07 - 1 + 4 + 91 - 2 + 1)^4 \\ &:= (-3 + 450 - 7 - 14 + 9 - 1 - 2 - 1)^4 \\ &:= (-3 + 450 + 7 - 14 - 9 - 1 + 2 - 1)^4 \\ &:= (-3 + 450 + 7 - 14 - 9 + 1 - 2 + 1)^4 \\ &:= (-3 + 450 - 7 - 1 - 4 + 9 - 12 - 1)^4 \\ &:= (-3 + 450 + 7 + 1 - 4 - 9 - 12 + 1)^4 \\ &:= (3 + 450 - 7 + 1 + 4 - 9 - 12 + 1)^4 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} &:= (3 + 4 + 507 + 1 + 4 - 91 + 2 + 1)^4 \\ &:= (-3 + 4 - 50 - 7 - 1 + 491 - 2 - 1)^4 \\ &:= (3 - 4 - 50 - 7 + 1 + 491 - 2 - 1)^4 \\ &:= (3 - 4 - 50 - 7 - 1 + 491 - 2 + 1)^4 \\ &:= (-3 - 4 - 50 - 7 + 1 + 491 + 2 + 1)^4 \\ &:= (3 + 4 + 5 - 071 + 491 - 2 + 1)^4 \\ &:= (345 + 071 + 4 - 9 - 1 + 21)^4 \\ &:= (3 + 450 - 71 + 49 - 1 + 2 - 1)^4 \\ &:= (3 + 450 - 71 + 49 + 1 - 2 + 1)^4 \\ &:= (3 + 450 - 7 + 14 - 9 + 1 - 21)^4 \\ &:= (3 - 4 + 507 - 1 - 4 - 91 + 21)^4 \end{aligned}$$

$$\mathbf{34518601216} := (3451 - 8 - 60 - 121 - 6)^3$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{34828517376} &:= (348 + 2 + 8 + 51 + 7 + 3 + 7 + 6)^4 \\ &:= (348 - 2 + 8 + 5 - 1 + 73 + 7 - 6)^4 \\ &:= (348 - 2 + 8 + 5 + 1 + 73 - 7 + 6)^4 \\ &:= (348 + 2 - 8 + 5 - 1 + 73 + 7 + 6)^4 \\ &:= (348 + 2 + 8 - 5 - 1 + 7 - 3 + 76)^4 \\ &:= (348 - 2 + 8 + 5 + 1 - 7 + 3 + 76)^4 \\ &:= (348 + 2 - 8 + 5 - 1 + 7 + 3 + 76)^4 \\ &:= (3 + 48 - 2 + 8 + 5 + 1 - 7 + 376)^4 \\ &:= (-3 + 48 + 2 + 8 - 5 - 1 + 7 + 376)^4 \\ &:= (3 + 48 + 2 - 8 + 5 - 1 + 7 + 376)^4 \\ &:= (3 - 4 - 82 + 8 + 517 + 3 - 7 - 6)^4 \\ &:= (3 + 4 - 82 - 8 + 517 - 3 + 7 - 6)^4 \\ &:= (-3 + 4 - 82 - 8 + 517 + 3 + 7 - 6)^4 \\ &:= (-3 - 4 - 82 + 8 + 517 - 3 - 7 + 6)^4 \\ &:= (-3 - 4 + 82 - 8 - 5 + 1 - 7 + 376)^4 \\ &:= (3 + 4 + 8 + 28 + 5 + 1 + 7 + 376)^4 \\ &:= (348 + 28 + 51 + 7 - 3 + 7 - 6)^4 \\ &:= (348 + 28 - 5 + 1 + 73 - 7 - 6)^4 \\ &:= (348 + 28 + 5 + 1 + 7 + 37 + 6)^4 \\ &:= (348 - 2 + 85 + 17 - 3 - 7 - 6)^4 \\ &:= (-3 + 482 + 8 + 5 - 17 - 37 - 6)^4 \\ &:= (3 + 482 + 8 - 5 + 17 + 3 - 76)^4 \\ &:= (-3 - 4 + 828 - 5 - 1 - 7 - 376)^4 \\ &:= (-3 - 4 - 8 - 285 + 1 + 737 - 6)^4 \\ &:= (3 + 4 - 8 + 285 - 1 + 73 + 76)^4 \\ &:= (-34 + 8 - 28 + 517 - 37 + 6)^4 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 &:= (34 - 8 - 28 + 51 + 7 + 376)^4 && := (354 + 7 + 7 + 9 - 8 - 2 + 73 - 6)^4 \\
 &:= (3 - 482 + 851 + 73 - 7 - 6)^4 && := (354 - 7 - 7 + 9 + 8 - 2 + 73 + 6)^4 \\
 &:= (-3 - 482 + 851 - 7 - 3 + 76)^4 && := (354 + 7 - 7 - 9 + 8 + 2 + 73 + 6)^4 \\
 &:= (3 + 48 + 285 + 17 + 3 + 76)^4 && := (354 - 7 + 7 - 9 + 8 + 2 + 73 + 6)^4 \\
 \mathbf{34837625096} &:= (3 - 4 + 8 + 3762 - 509 + 6)^3 && := (-3 - 5 + 477 + 9 - 8 - 27 - 3 - 6)^4 \\
 \mathbf{34869635163} &:= (-348 + 6 + 96 + 3516 - 3)^3 && := (3 - 5 + 477 - 9 - 8 - 27 - 3 + 6)^4 \\
 \mathbf{34933714109} &:= (-3 - 49 + 3371 - 41 - 09)^3 && := (-3 - 5 + 477 - 9 - 8 - 27 + 3 + 6)^4 \\
 \mathbf{34965783000} &:= (349 - 6 + 5 - 78 + 3000)^3 && := (354 + 7 - 7 + 98 - 27 + 3 + 6)^4 \\
 \mathbf{35010152100} &:= (35010 + 152100)^2 && := (354 - 7 + 7 + 98 - 27 + 3 + 6)^4 \\
 \mathbf{35152125121} &:= (351 + 52 + 1 + 25 + 1 + 2 + 1)^4 && := (354 + 7 - 7 + 9 + 8 + 27 + 36)^4 \\
 &:= (351 + 52 + 1 + 2 + 5 + 1 + 21)^4 && := (354 - 7 + 7 + 9 + 8 + 27 + 36)^4 \\
 &:= (351 + 5 + 21 + 2 + 51 + 2 + 1)^4 && := (35 + 477 - 9 + 8 + 2 - 73 - 6)^4 \\
 &:= (351 + 5 + 2 + 1 + 2 + 51 + 21)^4 && := (3 + 547 - 79 + 8 - 2 - 7 - 36)^4 \\
 &:= (-35 - 1 + 521 + 2 - 51 - 2 - 1)^4 && := (3 + 54 + 7 - 7 + 98 + 273 + 6)^4 \\
 &:= (-35 - 1 + 521 - 2 - 51 + 2 - 1)^4 && := (3 + 54 - 7 + 7 + 98 + 273 + 6)^4 \\
 &:= (-35 + 1 + 521 - 2 - 51 - 2 + 1)^4 && := (-35 + 477 + 9 - 8 + 27 - 36)^4 \\
 &:= (-3 - 51 - 5 - 21 + 2 + 512 - 1)^4 && := (-35 + 477 - 9 - 8 - 27 + 36)^4 \\
 &:= (351 + 52 + 12 + 5 + 12 + 1)^4 && := (3 + 5 - 477 + 982 - 73 - 6)^4 \\
 &:= (35 + 1 + 521 + 2 - 5 - 121)^4 && := (-3 - 5 + 477 - 98 + 27 + 36)^4 \\
 &:= (3 + 5 + 152 + 1 + 251 + 21)^4 && \\
 &:= (35 + 152 + 125 + 121)^4 && \mathbf{35546383872} := (3 - 554 + 6 + 3838 - 7 + 2)^3 \\
 & && := (3 + 55 - 4 - 638 + 3872)^3 \\
 \mathbf{35255286639} &:= (3525 - 5 - 286 + 6 + 39)^3 && \mathbf{35578826569} := (3557 + 8 - 8 - 265 + 6 - 9)^3 \\
 &:= (352 + 55 + 2866 - 3 + 9)^3 && := (3557 - 8 + 8 - 265 + 6 - 9)^3 \\
 &:= (-3 + 5 + 2552 + 86 + 639)^3 && := (-3 + 557 + 88 + 2656 - 9)^3 \\
 \mathbf{35287552000} &:= (3528 + 7 - 55 - 200 + 0)^3 && \mathbf{35611289000} := (3 - 5611 - 2 + 8900 + 0)^3 \\
 &:= (3 + 5287 - 5 - 5 - 2000)^3 && \\
 &:= (-3 + 528 + 755 + 2000)^3 && \mathbf{35723051649} := (35 + 72 - 3 + 05 + 1 + 6 + 4 + 9)^5 \\
 & && := (3 + 57 + 2 - 3 + 051 + 6 + 4 + 9)^5 \\
 \mathbf{35477982736} &:= (-3 - 5 + 477 - 9 - 8 - 2 - 7 - 3 - 6)^4 && := (-3 + 57 + 2 + 3 + 051 + 6 + 4 + 9)^5 \\
 &:= (354 + 77 + 9 + 8 + 2 - 7 - 3 - 6)^4 && := (-3 + 5 + 72 + 30 + 5 + 1 + 6 + 4 + 9)^5 \\
 &:= (354 + 77 + 9 - 8 - 2 + 7 + 3 - 6)^4 && := (3 + 5 + 72 - 3 + 051 + 6 + 4 - 9)^5 \\
 &:= (354 + 77 - 9 + 8 + 2 - 7 + 3 + 6)^4 && := (-3 + 5 + 72 + 3 + 051 + 6 + 4 - 9)^5 \\
 &:= (354 + 7 + 79 + 8 + 2 - 7 - 3 - 6)^4 && := (3 - 5 + 72 - 3 + 051 + 6 - 4 + 9)^5 \\
 &:= (354 - 7 + 79 + 8 + 2 + 7 - 3 - 6)^4 && := (-3 - 5 + 72 + 3 + 051 + 6 - 4 + 9)^5 \\
 &:= (354 + 7 + 79 - 8 - 2 + 7 + 3 - 6)^4 && := (-3 + 5 + 72 - 3 + 051 - 6 + 4 + 9)^5 \\
 &:= (354 - 7 + 79 + 8 - 2 - 7 + 3 + 6)^4 && := (35 + 7 - 2 + 30 + 5 - 1 + 64 - 9)^5 \\
 &:= (354 + 7 - 7 + 98 - 2 - 7 - 3 - 6)^4 && := (35 - 7 + 2 + 30 - 5 + 1 + 64 + 9)^5 \\
 &:= (354 - 7 + 7 + 98 - 2 - 7 - 3 - 6)^4 && := (35 + 7 - 2 + 30 + 5 - 1 + 6 + 49)^5 \\
 &:= (354 - 7 - 7 + 98 - 2 + 7 - 3 - 6)^4 && := (35 - 7 - 2 - 3 + 051 + 64 - 9)^5
 \end{aligned}$$

$:= (35 - 7 - 2 - 3 + 051 + 6 + 49)^5$	$:= (361 + 3 + 64 + 8 - 9 + 2 + 1 + 6)^4$
$:= (-3 + 57 + 23 + 051 + 6 + 4 - 9)^5$	$:= (361 + 3 + 6 + 48 + 9 + 2 + 1 + 6)^4$
$:= (3 + 57 + 2 + 30 - 5 - 1 - 6 + 49)^5$	$:= (361 - 3 - 6 + 4 + 89 - 2 - 1 - 6)^4$
$:= (-3 + 57 - 2 + 30 + 5 - 1 - 6 + 49)^5$	$:= (361 + 3 - 6 - 4 + 89 - 2 + 1 - 6)^4$
$:= (3 - 57 + 2 + 3 + 05 + 164 + 9)^5$	$:= (-36 + 1 - 3 - 6 + 489 - 2 - 1 - 6)^4$
$:= (3 + 57 + 2 - 3 + 05 + 16 + 49)^5$	$:= (-36 - 1 - 3 - 6 + 489 - 2 + 1 - 6)^4$
$:= (-3 + 57 + 2 + 3 + 05 + 16 + 49)^5$	$:= (3 + 61 + 364 + 8 + 9 - 2 - 1 - 6)^4$
$:= (3 + 5 + 72 - 30 + 5 + 1 + 64 + 9)^5$	$:= (-3 + 61 + 364 + 8 + 9 + 2 + 1 - 6)^4$
$:= (-3 + 5 - 7 - 2 + 30 + 51 + 64 - 9)^5$	$:= (3 + 61 + 364 - 8 + 9 + 2 - 1 + 6)^4$
$:= (3 - 5 - 7 + 2 + 30 + 51 + 64 - 9)^5$	$:= (3 + 61 + 364 + 8 - 9 + 2 + 1 + 6)^4$
$:= (-3 + 5 - 7 - 2 + 30 + 51 + 6 + 49)^5$	$:= (-3 - 6 + 1 + 364 + 89 - 2 - 1 - 6)^4$
$:= (3 - 5 - 7 + 2 + 30 + 51 + 6 + 49)^5$	$:= (-3 - 6 - 1 + 364 + 89 - 2 + 1 - 6)^4$
$:= (3 + 5 - 7 - 2 - 30 + 5 + 164 - 9)^5$	$:= (-3 - 6 + 1 - 36 + 489 - 2 - 1 - 6)^4$
$:= (35 + 72 - 30 + 51 + 6 + 4 - 9)^5$	$:= (-3 - 6 - 1 - 36 + 489 - 2 + 1 - 6)^4$
$:= (-35 + 72 + 30 + 51 + 6 - 4 + 9)^5$	$:= (361 - 36 + 4 + 8 + 92 + 1 + 6)^4$
$:= (35 + 72 + 30 - 5 - 16 + 4 + 9)^5$	$:= (361 + 36 + 4 + 8 + 9 + 2 + 16)^4$
$:= (-35 - 7 + 230 - 5 + 1 - 64 + 9)^5$	$:= (361 - 3 + 64 + 8 - 9 + 21 - 6)^4$
$:= (-35 - 7 + 230 - 5 + 1 - 6 - 49)^5$	$:= (361 - 3 + 6 + 48 + 9 + 21 - 6)^4$
$:= (35 - 7 - 23 + 051 + 64 + 9)^5$	$:= (361 + 3 + 6 + 48 - 9 + 21 + 6)^4$
$:= (3 - 57 + 230 - 5 + 1 + 6 - 49)^5$	$:= (361 - 3 - 6 + 48 + 9 + 21 + 6)^4$
$:= (3 - 57 + 23 + 05 + 164 - 9)^5$	$:= (361 + 3 + 6 + 4 + 89 - 21 - 6)^4$
$:= (3 - 5 + 7 + 230 - 51 - 64 + 9)^5$	$:= (361 + 3 - 6 + 4 + 89 - 21 + 6)^4$
$:= (3 - 5 + 7 + 230 - 51 - 6 - 49)^5$	$:= (361 - 3 + 6 + 4 - 8 + 92 - 16)^4$
$:= (-3 - 5 + 7 - 2 + 305 - 164 - 9)^5$	$:= (-36 + 1 + 364 + 8 + 92 + 1 + 6)^4$
$:= (-3 + 5 - 7 + 2 + 305 - 164 - 9)^5$	$:= (36 + 1 + 364 + 8 + 9 + 2 + 16)^4$
$:= (357 - 230 + 5 - 16 + 4 + 9)^5$	$:= (-36 + 1 + 3 + 6 + 489 - 21 - 6)^4$
$:= (35 + 72 + 30 - 51 - 6 + 49)^5$	$:= (-36 + 1 + 3 - 6 + 489 - 21 + 6)^4$
35741336184 $:= (-3 - 57 + 4 + 1 + 3361 - 8 - 4)^3$	$:= (-3 + 61 + 364 + 8 - 9 + 21 - 6)^4$
$:= (-3 - 57 - 4 + 1 + 3361 - 8 + 4)^3$	$:= (3 - 61 - 3 - 6 + 489 - 2 + 16)^4$
$:= (-3 + 5 - 74 + 1 + 3361 + 8 - 4)^3$	$:= (-3 - 61 + 3 - 6 + 489 - 2 + 16)^4$
35773897375 $:= (3577 - 3 + 89 + 7 - 375)^3$	$:= (3 + 6 + 1 + 364 + 89 - 21 - 6)^4$
36002379608 $:= (3600 - 237 - 9 - 60 + 8)^3$	$:= (3 - 6 + 1 + 364 + 89 - 21 + 6)^4$
36101900025 $:= (3 + 6 - 1 + 0190002 - 5)^2$	$:= (-3 + 6 + 1 + 364 - 8 + 92 - 16)^4$
$:= (3 - 6 + 1 + 0190002 + 5)^2$	$:= (3 + 6 + 1 - 36 + 489 - 21 - 6)^4$
36133376616 $:= (-36 + 1 + 3337 - 6 - 6 + 16)^3$	$:= (3 - 6 + 1 - 36 + 489 - 21 + 6)^4$
36136489216 $:= (361 + 3 + 64 + 8 + 9 - 2 - 1 - 6)^4$	$:= (3 + 6 + 1 + 3 + 648 - 9 - 216)^4$
$:= (361 - 3 + 64 + 8 + 9 + 2 + 1 - 6)^4$	$:= (3 - 6 + 1 - 3 + 648 + 9 - 216)^4$
$:= (361 + 3 + 64 - 8 + 9 + 2 - 1 + 6)^4$	$:= (-3 - 6 + 1 + 3 + 648 + 9 - 216)^4$

$$\begin{aligned} &:= (361 + 36 - 48 + 92 + 1 - 6)^4 \\ &:= (361 + 36 + 48 + 9 - 2 - 16)^4 \\ &:= (361 - 36 + 4 + 89 + 2 + 16)^4 \\ &:= (-36 + 1 + 364 + 89 + 2 + 16)^4 \\ &:= (-36 + 1 - 36 + 489 + 2 + 16)^4 \\ &:= (3 + 613 - 64 - 89 - 21 - 6)^4 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} &:= (3 + 613 - 64 - 8 - 92 - 16)^4 \\ &:= (3 + 61 + 3 + 64 + 89 + 216)^4 \\ &:= (-3 - 6 + 1364 + 8 - 921 - 6)^4 \\ &:= (-3 - 6 + 136 + 4 + 89 + 216)^4 \end{aligned}$$

$$\mathbf{36198994112} := (3619 + 89 + 9 - 411 + 2)^3$$

$$:= (-36 + 469 + 1 - 5 - 8 + 9 + 6 + 1)^4$$

$$\mathbf{36231832629} := (36 - 2 - 3 - 1 + 8 + 3262 + 9)^3$$

$$:= (-3 - 6 + 469 - 15 + 8 - 9 - 6 - 1)^4$$

$$:= (3 - 6 + 2 + 31 + 8 + 3262 + 9)^3$$

$$:= (3 + 6 + 469 + 1 - 58 + 9 + 6 + 1)^4$$

$$:= (-3 + 62 - 3 - 18 + 3262 + 9)^3$$

$$:= (364 - 6 - 9 - 15 + 8 + 96 - 1)^4$$

$$:= (3 - 6 + 23 + 18 + 3262 + 9)^3$$

$$:= (36 + 469 - 1 - 5 + 8 - 9 - 61)^4$$

$$\mathbf{36297569231} := (36 + 2975 + 69 + 231)^3$$

$$:= (3 - 6 + 469 + 15 + 8 + 9 - 61)^4$$

$$\mathbf{36330467328} := (3 - 6 + 3304 - 6 - 7 + 32 - 8)^3$$

$$:= (-3 + 6 - 469 + 1 + 5 + 896 + 1)^4$$

$$:= (-36 + 3304 + 6 + 7 + 3 + 28)^3$$

$$:= (-364 + 691 + 5 + 8 + 96 + 1)^4$$

$$\mathbf{36363385297} := (3 - 63 + 6 + 3385 - 2 - 9 - 7)^3$$

$$:= (364 - 69 + 158 - 9 - 6 - 1)^4$$

$$:= (-3 - 63 - 6 + 3385 - 2 + 9 - 7)^3$$

$$:= (364 - 6 + 91 + 58 - 9 - 61)^4$$

$$:= (-3 - 63 - 6 + 3385 + 2 - 9 + 7)^3$$

$$:= (364 - 6 - 9 + 158 - 9 - 61)^4$$

$$:= (-36 - 36 + 3385 - 2 + 9 - 7)^3$$

$$:= (-364 + 691 + 58 - 9 + 61)^4$$

$$:= (-36 - 36 + 3385 + 2 - 9 + 7)^3$$

$$\mathbf{36528273432} := (-36 - 5 + 2 - 82 + 7 + 3432)^3$$

$$:= (36 - 3 - 6 + 3385 - 2 - 97)^3$$

$$:= (-3 + 65 + 2827 - 3 + 432)^3$$

$$:= (-3 - 6 + 36 + 3385 - 2 - 97)^3$$

$$\mathbf{36594368000} := (-365 + 9 - 4 + 3680 + 00)^3$$

$$:= (-36 + 3633 + 8 + 5 - 297)^3$$

$$\mathbf{36804120336} := (-3 - 6 + 8 + 0412 + 033 - 6)^4$$

$$:= (3 - 636 - 3 + 3852 + 97)^3$$

$$:= (368 + 041 + 2 + 033 - 6)^4$$

$$:= (-3 - 636 + 3 + 3852 + 97)^3$$

$$:= (-3 + 68 + 0412 - 033 - 6)^4$$

$$:= (-363 - 6 + 3385 + 297)^3$$

$$:= (-3 + 68 + 0412 - 03 - 36)^4$$

$$\mathbf{36396323144} := (-3 + 63 + 9 + 6 + 3231 + 4 + 4)^3$$

$$:= (3 - 6 + 80 + 4 + 1 + 20 + 336)^4$$

$$:= (3639 - 6 - 3 + 2 - 314 - 4)^3$$

$$:= (-3 - 6 + 804 - 1 - 20 - 336)^4$$

$$:= (36 - 3 + 963 + 2314 + 4)^3$$

$$:= (36 - 804 + 1203 - 3 + 6)^4$$

$$\mathbf{36429280875} := (-3 + 6 + 429 + 2808 + 75)^3$$

$$:= (-3 + 6 - 804 + 1203 + 36)^4$$

$$\mathbf{36469158961} := (364 + 69 - 1 - 5 + 8 + 9 - 6 - 1)^4$$

$$\mathbf{36859543552} := (3685 + 9 - 5 - 4 - 355 - 2)^3$$

$$:= (364 + 69 + 1 - 5 - 8 + 9 + 6 + 1)^4$$

$$:= (3685 - 9 + 5 + 4 - 355 - 2)^3$$

$$:= (364 + 6 - 9 - 1 - 5 + 89 - 6 - 1)^4$$

$$\mathbf{36892780289} := (3689 + 2 + 7 - 80 - 289)^3$$

$$:= (364 - 6 - 9 + 1 + 5 + 89 - 6 - 1)^4$$

$$\mathbf{36926037000} := (36 - 9 + 2603 + 700 + 0)^3$$

$$:= (364 - 6 - 9 - 1 - 5 + 89 + 6 - 1)^4$$

$$\mathbf{36959313691} := (36 + 9 + 59 + 3136 + 91)^3$$

$$:= (364 - 6 - 9 - 1 + 5 + 89 - 6 + 1)^4$$

$$\mathbf{37025927037} := (-3702 + 5 - 9 + 2 + 7037)^3$$

$$:= (364 + 6 + 9 + 1 - 5 - 8 + 9 + 61)^4$$

$$\mathbf{37059263704} := (3705 - 9 - 2 + 6 - 370 + 4)^3$$

$$:= (-36 + 469 - 1 - 5 + 8 + 9 - 6 - 1)^4$$

$$:= (-370 - 5 + 9 + 2 - 6 + 3704)^3$$

$:= (-370 + 5 - 9 - 2 + 6 + 3704)^3$ $:= (-3 + 705 - 9 + 2637 + 04)^3$ $\mathbf{37092620375} := (-3 + 709 + 2620 - 3 + 7 + 5)^3$ $\mathbf{37125997056} := (37 + 1 + 2599 + 705 - 6)^3$ $\mathbf{37129300000} := (-3 + 7 + 129 - 3 + 0000 + 0)^5$ $\mathbf{37141383841} := (371 + 41 + 3 + 8 + 3 + 8 + 4 + 1)^4$ $:= (371 - 4 - 1 + 3 + 83 - 8 - 4 - 1)^4$ $:= (371 - 4 + 1 - 3 - 8 - 3 + 84 + 1)^4$ $:= (371 + 4 + 1 + 3 + 8 + 3 + 8 + 41)^4$ $:= (37 - 1 + 413 - 8 + 3 - 8 + 4 - 1)^4$ $:= (37 + 1 + 4 + 1 + 383 + 8 + 4 + 1)^4$ $:= (37 + 1 + 4 + 1 + 3 + 8 + 384 + 1)^4$ $:= (3 + 71 - 4 - 1 + 383 - 8 - 4 - 1)^4$ $:= (-3 + 71 - 4 + 1 - 3 - 8 + 384 + 1)^4$ $:= (-3 - 7 + 1 + 413 - 8 + 38 + 4 + 1)^4$ $:= (3 + 7 + 1 + 4 + 1 + 38 + 384 + 1)^4$ $:= (371 + 4 + 13 + 8 + 38 + 4 + 1)^4$ $:= (371 - 4 + 1 + 38 + 38 - 4 - 1)^4$ $:= (371 - 4 - 1 + 38 + 38 - 4 + 1)^4$ $:= (3 - 71 + 413 + 83 + 8 + 4 - 1)^4$ $:= (3 - 71 + 413 + 8 + 3 + 84 - 1)^4$ $:= (3 + 7 + 14 - 1 + 383 - 8 + 41)^4$ $:= (3 + 7 + 1 - 413 + 838 + 4 - 1)^4$ $:= (3 + 7 - 1 - 413 + 838 + 4 + 1)^4$ $:= (37 + 14 + 13 - 8 + 384 - 1)^4$ $:= (3 - 71 + 41 + 383 + 84 - 1)^4$ $:= (3 - 7 - 14 - 1 - 383 + 841)^4$ $\mathbf{37192810472} := (37 + 19 + 2810 + 472)^3$ $\mathbf{37293180821} := (-3 + 72 + 9 + 3180 + 82 + 1)^3$ $\mathbf{37326677688} := (3 - 7 + 3266 - 7 - 7 + 6 + 88)^3$ $\mathbf{37393731584} := (3739 - 3 + 7 - 315 - 84)^3$ $\mathbf{37427288625} := (-3 + 7 - 4 + 2728 - 8 + 625)^3$ $:= (3 - 7 + 4 + 2728 - 8 + 625)^3$ $\mathbf{37480960000} := (-37 + 480 - 9 + 6 + 0000)^4$ $:= (3 - 74 - 80 - 9 + 600 + 00)^4$ $\mathbf{37822859361} := (37 - 8 - 2 - 2 - 8 + 5 + 9 - 3 - 6 - 1)^8$ $:= (37 - 8 + 2 - 2 - 8 - 5 + 9 + 3 - 6 - 1)^8$ $:= (37 - 8 - 2 + 2 - 8 - 5 + 9 + 3 - 6 - 1)^8$	$:= (37 + 8 - 2 - 2 - 8 - 5 - 9 - 3 + 6 - 1)^8$ $:= (37 - 8 - 2 - 2 + 8 - 5 - 9 - 3 + 6 - 1)^8$ $:= (37 - 8 - 2 - 2 - 8 + 5 - 9 + 3 + 6 - 1)^8$ $:= (37 + 8 - 2 - 2 - 8 + 5 - 9 - 3 - 6 + 1)^8$ $:= (37 - 8 - 2 - 2 + 8 + 5 - 9 - 3 - 6 + 1)^8$ $:= (37 - 8 + 2 + 2 - 8 - 5 + 9 - 3 - 6 + 1)^8$ $:= (37 + 8 + 2 - 2 - 8 - 5 - 9 + 3 - 6 + 1)^8$ $:= (37 + 8 - 2 + 2 - 8 - 5 - 9 + 3 - 6 + 1)^8$ $:= (37 - 8 + 2 - 2 + 8 - 5 - 9 + 3 - 6 + 1)^8$ $:= (37 - 8 - 2 + 2 + 8 - 5 - 9 + 3 - 6 + 1)^8$ $:= (37 - 8 + 2 - 2 - 8 + 5 - 9 - 3 + 6 + 1)^8$ $:= (37 - 8 - 2 + 2 - 8 + 5 - 9 - 3 + 6 + 1)^8$ $:= (37 - 8 + 2 + 2 - 8 - 5 - 9 + 3 + 6 + 1)^8$ $:= (-3 - 7 - 8 - 2 - 2 - 8 + 59 - 3 - 6 + 1)^8$ $:= (-3 + 7 + 8 - 2 - 2 - 8 - 5 - 9 + 36 - 1)^8$ $:= (3 - 7 + 8 + 2 + 2 - 8 - 5 - 9 + 36 - 1)^8$ $:= (-3 + 7 - 8 - 2 - 2 + 8 - 5 - 9 + 36 - 1)^8$ $:= (3 - 7 - 8 + 2 + 2 + 8 - 5 - 9 + 36 - 1)^8$ $:= (3 + 7 - 8 - 2 - 2 - 8 + 5 - 9 + 36 - 1)^8$ $:= (-3 - 7 + 8 + 2 - 2 - 8 + 5 - 9 + 36 - 1)^8$ $:= (-3 - 7 + 8 - 2 + 2 - 8 + 5 - 9 + 36 - 1)^8$ $:= (-3 - 7 - 8 + 2 - 2 + 8 + 5 - 9 + 36 - 1)^8$ $:= (-3 - 7 - 8 - 2 + 2 + 8 + 5 - 9 + 36 - 1)^8$ $:= (3 + 7 - 8 + 2 + 2 - 8 - 5 - 9 + 36 + 1)^8$ $:= (-3 + 7 - 8 + 2 - 2 - 8 + 5 - 9 + 36 + 1)^8$ $:= (-3 + 7 - 8 - 2 + 2 - 8 + 5 - 9 + 36 + 1)^8$ $:= (3 - 7 - 8 + 2 - 2 - 8 - 5 + 9 + 36 + 1)^8$ $:= (3 - 7 - 8 - 2 + 2 - 8 - 5 + 9 + 36 + 1)^8$ $:= (-3 - 7 - 8 - 2 - 2 - 8 + 5 + 9 + 36 + 1)^8$ $:= (-37 + 82 - 2 - 8 + 5 - 9 - 3 - 6 - 1)^8$ $:= (-37 + 82 + 2 - 8 - 5 - 9 + 3 - 6 - 1)^8$ $:= (37 + 8 - 22 - 8 - 5 + 9 - 3 + 6 - 1)^8$ $:= (37 - 8 - 22 + 8 - 5 + 9 - 3 + 6 - 1)^8$ $:= (37 - 8 - 22 - 8 + 5 + 9 + 3 + 6 - 1)^8$ $:= (37 - 8 + 22 - 8 - 5 - 9 - 3 - 6 + 1)^8$ $:= (37 + 8 - 22 - 8 + 5 + 9 - 3 - 6 + 1)^8$ $:= (37 - 8 - 22 + 8 + 5 + 9 - 3 - 6 + 1)^8$ $:= (37 + 8 - 22 + 8 - 5 - 9 - 3 + 6 + 1)^8$
--	--

$$\begin{aligned} &:= (37+8-22-8+5-9+3+6+1)^8 \\ &:= (37-8-22+8+5-9+3+6+1)^8 \\ &:= (37+8-2-28-5+9-3+6-1)^8 \\ &:= (37-8-2-28+5+9+3+6-1)^8 \\ &:= (37+8-2-28+5+9-3-6+1)^8 \\ &:= (37+8+2-28-5+9+3-6+1)^8 \\ &:= (37-8+2-28+5+9-3+6+1)^8 \\ &:= (37+8-2-28+5-9+3+6+1)^8 \\ &:= (-37+8-2+28+5+9+3+6+1)^8 \\ &:= (-37-8+2-2+85-9-3-6-1)^8 \\ &:= (-37-8-2+2+85-9-3-6-1)^8 \\ &:= (-37+8+2+2-8+5-9-3+61)^8 \\ &:= (-37-8+2+2+8+5-9-3+61)^8 \\ &:= (-37+8-2-2-8-5+9-3+61)^8 \\ &:= (-37-8-2-2+8-5+9-3+61)^8 \\ &:= (-37-8-2-2-8+5+9+3+61)^8 \\ &:= (-3+78-22-8-5-9-3-6-1)^8 \\ &:= (-3+78-2-28-5-9-3-6-1)^8 \\ &:= (3-78+2-2+85+9-3+6-1)^8 \\ &:= (3-78-2+2+85+9-3+6-1)^8 \\ &:= (-3-78+2-2+85+9+3+6-1)^8 \\ &:= (-3-78-2+2+85+9+3+6-1)^8 \\ &:= (3-78+2+2+85+9+3-6+1)^8 \\ &:= (-3-78+2+2+85+9-3+6+1)^8 \\ &:= (3+78+2-2+8+5-9-3-61)^8 \\ &:= (3+78-2+2+8+5-9-3-61)^8 \\ &:= (-3+78+2+2-8+5+9-3-61)^8 \\ &:= (3+78+2+2+8-5-9+3-61)^8 \\ &:= (-3+78+2-2+8+5-9+3-61)^8 \\ &:= (-3+78-2+2+8+5-9+3-61)^8 \\ &:= (3-7+82-2+8-59+3-6-1)^8 \\ &:= (-3-7+82-2+8-59-3+6-1)^8 \\ &:= (3-7+82+2-8-59+3+6-1)^8 \\ &:= (3-7+82+2+8-59-3-6+1)^8 \\ &:= (3+7+82-2-8-59+3-6+1)^8 \\ &:= (-3-7+82+2+8-59+3-6+1)^8 \\ &:= (-3+7+82-2-8-59-3+6+1)^8 \\ &:= (-3+7-82-2+8-5+93+6-1)^8 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} &:= (3+7-82-2-8+5+93+6-1)^8 \\ &:= (-3-7-82+2+8+5+93+6-1)^8 \\ &:= (3+7-82+2+8-5+93-6+1)^8 \\ &:= (-3+7-82-2+8+5+93-6+1)^8 \\ &:= (3+7+82+2+8+5-93+6+1)^8 \\ &:= (-3+7-82+2-8+5+93+6+1)^8 \\ &:= (3-7+82+2-8-5-9-36-1)^8 \\ &:= (-3-7+82-2-8+5-9-36-1)^8 \\ &:= (3+7-8-22-8+59-3-6-1)^8 \\ &:= (-3+7-8-22-8+59+3-6-1)^8 \\ &:= (3-7-8-22-8+59-3+6+1)^8 \\ &:= (-3-7-8-22-8+59+3+6+1)^8 \\ &:= (3-7+8-22+8+5-9+36-1)^8 \\ &:= (-3+7+8-22-8-5+9+36-1)^8 \\ &:= (-3+7-8-22+8-5+9+36-1)^8 \\ &:= (3+7-8-22-8+5+9+36-1)^8 \\ &:= (-3+7+8+22+8+5+9-36+1)^8 \\ &:= (-3+7+8-22+8-5-9+36+1)^8 \\ &:= (3+7+8-22-8+5-9+36+1)^8 \\ &:= (3+7-8-22+8+5-9+36+1)^8 \\ &:= (3+7-8-2-28+59-3-6-1)^8 \\ &:= (-3-7+8+2-28+59-3-6-1)^8 \\ &:= (-3+7-8-2-28+59+3-6-1)^8 \\ &:= (-3+7-8+2-28+59-3-6+1)^8 \\ &:= (3-7-8-2-28+59-3+6+1)^8 \\ &:= (-3-7-8-2-28+59+3+6+1)^8 \\ &:= (3+7+8-2+28+5+9-36-1)^8 \\ &:= (-3+7+8-2-28-5+9+36-1)^8 \\ &:= (3+7-8-2-28+5+9+36-1)^8 \\ &:= (-3-7+8+2-28+5+9+36-1)^8 \\ &:= (-3+7+8+2+28+5+9-36+1)^8 \\ &:= (3+7+8-2-28+5-9+36+1)^8 \\ &:= (-3+7-8+2-28+5+9+36+1)^8 \\ &:= (-3+7+8-2-2-85+93+6-1)^8 \\ &:= (3-7+8+2+2-85+93+6-1)^8 \\ &:= (3+7+8+2-2-85+93-6+1)^8 \\ &:= (3+7+8-2+2-85+93-6+1)^8 \\ &:= (3+7+8+2+2+85-93+6+1)^8 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} &:= (3+7-8+2+2-85+93+6+1)^8 & &:= (-3-78-2+2+8+59+36-1)^8 \\ &:= (-3-7-8+2-2+85-9-36-1)^8 & &:= (-3+7+82+28-5-93+6-1)^8 \\ &:= (-3-7-8-2+2+85-9-36-1)^8 & &:= (-3+7+82+28+5-93-6+1)^8 \\ &:= (3+7+8+2-2+8+59-3-61)^8 & &:= (-3-7+82-28+5+9-36-1)^8 \\ &:= (3+7+8-2+2+8+59-3-61)^8 & &:= (3-7+82+2-85-9+36-1)^8 \\ &:= (-3+7+8+2-2+8+59+3-61)^8 & &:= (-3-7-82+2+85-9+36-1)^8 \\ &:= (-3+7+8-2+2+8+59+3-61)^8 & &:= (3-7-82-2-8+59-3+61)^8 \\ &:= (3+7+8-2-2+8-59-3+61)^8 & &:= (-3-7-82-2-8+59+3+61)^8 \\ &:= (-3+7+8-2-2+8-59+3+61)^8 & &:= (3-7+82-2+8+5-9+361)^4 \\ &:= (3-7+8+2+2+8-59+3+61)^8 & &:= (-3+7+82-2-8-5+9+361)^4 \\ &:= (3+7-8+2-2-8-5+93-61)^8 & &:= (-3-7+82+2-8+5+9+361)^4 \\ &:= (3+7-8-2+2-8-5+93-61)^8 & &:= (-3-7+8+22-85+93-6-1)^8 \\ &:= (-3-7+8+2+2-8-5+93-61)^8 & &:= (3+7-8+22+85-93+6-1)^8 \\ &:= (-3-7-8+2+2+8-5+93-61)^8 & &:= (-3+7+8+22+85-93-6+1)^8 \\ &:= (-3+7-8-2-2-8+5+93-61)^8 & &:= (-3+7-8+22-85+93-6+1)^8 \\ &:= (3-7-8+2+2-8+5+93-61)^8 & &:= (3-7+8-22+85-9-36-1)^8 \\ &:= (378+2-2+8+59+3-6-1)^4 & &:= (3+7-8-22+85-9-36+1)^8 \\ &:= (378-2+2+8+59+3-6-1)^4 & &:= (-3+7+8+22-8+59-3-61)^8 \\ &:= (378+2+2-8+59+3+6-1)^4 & &:= (-3+7-8+22+8+59-3-61)^8 \\ &:= (378+2+2+8+59-3-6+1)^4 & &:= (3+7-8+22-8-59+3+61)^8 \\ &:= (378+2+2+8+5+9+36+1)^4 & &:= (-3-7+8-22+8+5+93-61)^8 \\ &:= (-37+82-28+5+9-3-6-1)^8 & &:= (3+7+8+22+8+5-93+61)^8 \\ &:= (-37+82-28+5-9+3+6-1)^8 & &:= (-3+7-8+2+28+59-3-61)^8 \\ &:= (37-82-2+85-9-3-6+1)^8 & &:= (-3+7-8-2+28-59-3+61)^8 \\ &:= (37+82-2-85-9+3-6+1)^8 & &:= (3+7+8+2+28+5-93+61)^8 \\ &:= (37-82+2-8+5+9-3+61)^8 & &:= (3-7+8+2-2+85-9+361)^4 \\ &:= (37-82-2+8+5-9+3+61)^8 & &:= (3-7+8-2+2+85-9+361)^4 \\ &:= (-37+8-22+85-9+3-6-1)^8 & &:= (-3-7-8+2+2+85+9+361)^4 \\ &:= (37+8+22+8-5+9+3-61)^8 & &:= (378+22-8+59-3-6-1)^4 \\ &:= (37+8-2+28+5+9-3-61)^8 & &:= (378-22-8-5+93+6-1)^4 \\ &:= (37+8+2+28-5+9+3-61)^8 & &:= (378-22-8+5+93-6+1)^4 \\ &:= (37-8+2+2-85+9+3+61)^8 & &:= (378+22-8+5+9+36-1)^4 \\ &:= (3-78+22+85-9+3-6+1)^8 & &:= (378+22+8+5-9+36+1)^4 \\ &:= (-3-78+22+85-9-3+6+1)^8 & &:= (378-2-28-5+93+6-1)^4 \\ &:= (-3+78+22-8+5-9-3-61)^8 & &:= (378-2-28+5+93-6+1)^4 \\ &:= (-3-78+22+8+5+9-3+61)^8 & &:= (378+2+28+5-9+36+1)^4 \\ &:= (-3-78+2+28+5+9-3+61)^8 & &:= (378+2+2+85+9-36+1)^4 \\ &:= (-3-78+2-2+8+59+36-1)^8 & &:= (378+2-2+8+5-9-361)^8 \end{aligned}$$

$:= (378 - 2 + 2 + 8 + 5 - 9 - 361)^8$	$:= (-3 + 8 - 06 + 8 - 6 + 9 - 2 + 54 - 4)^6$
$:= (37 - 8 + 22 - 85 - 9 + 3 + 61)^8$	$:= (3 + 8 + 06 - 8 + 6 - 9 + 2 + 54 - 4)^6$
$:= (37 - 8 - 22 - 8 + 59 - 36 - 1)^8$	$:= (3 - 8 + 06 + 8 + 6 - 9 + 2 + 54 - 4)^6$
$:= (37 - 8 + 22 - 8 - 59 + 36 + 1)^8$	$:= (-3 + 8 + 06 - 8 - 6 + 9 + 2 + 54 - 4)^6$
$:= (-37 - 8 - 22 - 8 + 59 + 36 + 1)^8$	$:= (-3 - 8 + 06 + 8 - 6 + 9 + 2 + 54 - 4)^6$
$:= (37 - 8 - 2 - 28 + 59 - 36 - 1)^8$	$:= (-3 + 8 - 06 - 8 + 6 + 9 + 2 + 54 - 4)^6$
$:= (-37 + 8 - 2 + 28 + 59 - 36 + 1)^8$	$:= (-3 - 8 - 06 + 8 + 6 + 9 + 2 + 54 - 4)^6$
$:= (-37 - 8 - 2 - 28 + 59 + 36 + 1)^8$	$:= (-3 - 8 + 06 - 8 + 6 + 9 - 2 + 54 + 4)^6$
$:= (37 - 8 + 2 - 2 - 8 + 59 + 361)^4$	$:= (3 + 8 - 06 + 8 - 6 - 9 + 2 + 54 + 4)^6$
$:= (37 - 8 - 2 + 2 - 8 + 59 + 361)^4$	$:= (-38 + 06 + 86 + 9 - 2 + 5 - 4 - 4)^6$
$:= (-3 + 78 - 22 - 8 - 59 + 36 - 1)^8$	$:= (-38 - 06 + 86 + 9 + 2 + 5 + 4 - 4)^6$
$:= (3 + 78 + 2 + 285 + 9 + 3 + 61)^4$	$:= (-38 - 06 + 86 + 9 + 2 + 5 - 4 + 4)^6$
$:= (-3 + 78 - 2 - 28 - 59 + 36 - 1)^8$	$:= (38 + 06 - 8 + 6 - 9 + 25 + 4 - 4)^6$
$:= (-3 + 7 + 82 - 28 - 5 - 93 + 61)^8$	$:= (38 + 06 - 8 + 6 - 9 + 25 - 4 + 4)^6$
$:= (3 + 7 + 82 - 2 + 85 - 93 - 61)^8$	$:= (38 - 06 + 8 - 6 - 9 + 25 + 4 + 4)^6$
$:= (-3 - 7 + 82 + 2 - 85 + 93 - 61)^8$	$:= (38 + 06 - 8 - 6 - 9 - 2 - 5 + 44)^6$
$:= (-3 - 7 - 8 + 22 + 85 - 9 + 361)^4$	$:= (38 - 06 - 8 + 6 - 9 - 2 - 5 + 44)^6$
$:= (3 - 7 + 8 - 2 + 285 + 93 + 61)^4$	$:= (-3 + 80 + 6 + 8 + 6 + 9 + 2 - 54 + 4)^6$
$:= (378 + 22 + 85 - 9 - 36 + 1)^4$	$:= (-3 + 8 + 06 + 86 + 9 + 2 - 54 + 4)^6$
$:= (378 - 2 + 28 + 5 + 93 - 61)^4$	$:= (3 + 8 + 06 - 8 + 6 + 92 - 5 - 44)^6$
$:= (-37 - 82 - 28 + 593 - 6 + 1)^4$	$:= (3 - 8 + 06 + 8 + 6 + 92 - 5 - 44)^6$
$:= (37 - 82 - 28 + 59 + 36 - 1)^8$	$:= (38 + 068 - 6 - 9 - 25 - 4 - 4)^6$
$:= (3 + 78 - 228 + 593 - 6 + 1)^4$	$:= (-38 + 068 - 6 + 9 + 25 + 4 - 4)^6$
$:= (-37 - 82 + 28 + 593 - 61)^4$	$:= (-38 + 068 - 6 + 9 + 25 - 4 + 4)^6$
$:= (3 - 782 + 285 + 936 - 1)^4$	$:= (38 + 068 - 6 + 9 - 2 - 5 - 44)^6$
37933056000 $:= (-3 + 7 - 9 + 3305 + 60 + 00)^3$	$:= (-38 - 06 + 86 - 9 + 25 + 4 - 4)^6$
37966934881 $:= (37 - 96 - 69 + 3488 + 1)^3$	$:= (-38 - 06 + 86 - 9 + 25 - 4 + 4)^6$
38034753147 $:= (38 + 03475 - 3 - 147)^3$	$:= (38 - 06 + 86 - 9 - 2 - 5 - 44)^6$
38068692544 $:= (38 + 06 + 8 - 6 + 9 - 2 + 5 + 4 - 4)^6$	$:= (-38 - 06 + 8 + 69 + 25 + 4 - 4)^6$
$:= (38 - 06 + 8 + 6 + 9 - 2 + 5 + 4 - 4)^6$	$:= (-38 - 06 + 8 + 69 + 25 - 4 + 4)^6$
$:= (38 + 06 - 8 + 6 + 9 + 2 + 5 + 4 - 4)^6$	$:= (38 - 06 + 8 + 69 - 2 - 5 - 44)^6$
$:= (38 + 06 + 8 - 6 + 9 - 2 + 5 - 4 + 4)^6$	$:= (38 + 06 - 8 + 69 + 2 - 5 - 44)^6$
$:= (38 - 06 + 8 + 6 + 9 - 2 + 5 - 4 + 4)^6$	$:= (-38 - 06 - 8 + 69 + 2 - 5 + 44)^6$
$:= (38 + 06 - 8 + 6 + 9 + 2 + 5 - 4 + 4)^6$	$:= (38 + 06 - 8 - 6 + 9 - 25 + 44)^6$
$:= (38 - 06 + 8 - 6 + 9 + 2 + 5 + 4 + 4)^6$	$:= (38 - 06 - 8 + 6 + 9 - 25 + 44)^6$
$:= (-3 - 8 - 06 - 8 - 6 + 92 + 5 - 4 - 4)^6$	$:= (-3 - 80 + 68 - 6 + 92 - 5 - 4 - 4)^6$
$:= (3 + 8 + 06 + 8 - 6 - 9 - 2 + 54 - 4)^6$	$:= (3 + 80 + 68 - 6 - 92 + 5 + 4 - 4)^6$
$:= (3 + 8 - 06 + 8 + 6 - 9 - 2 + 54 - 4)^6$	$:= (3 + 80 + 68 - 6 - 92 + 5 - 4 + 4)^6$

$$\begin{aligned} &:= (-3 + 80 - 68 + 6 - 9 + 2 + 54 - 4)^6 \\ &:= (3 - 80 + 68 + 6 + 9 + 2 + 54 - 4)^6 \\ &:= (3 + 80 - 6 + 86 - 92 - 5 - 4 - 4)^6 \\ &:= (3 - 80 + 6 + 86 - 9 + 2 + 54 - 4)^6 \\ &:= (-3 + 80 + 6 - 86 + 9 + 2 + 54 - 4)^6 \\ &:= (-3 - 80 - 6 + 86 + 9 + 2 + 54 - 4)^6 \\ &:= (-3 + 80 - 6 + 8 - 69 - 2 + 54 - 4)^6 \\ &:= (-3 + 80 + 6 - 8 - 69 + 2 + 54 - 4)^6 \\ &:= (3 - 80 + 6 + 8 + 69 + 2 + 54 - 4)^6 \\ &:= (3 - 80 + 6 - 8 + 6 + 92 - 5 + 44)^6 \\ &:= (3 + 8 + 068 - 69 - 2 + 54 - 4)^6 \\ &:= (-3 + 8 - 068 + 69 + 2 + 54 - 4)^6 \\ &:= (-3 - 8 - 068 + 6 + 92 - 5 + 44)^6 \\ &:= (-38 + 068 + 69 - 2 + 5 - 44)^6 \\ &:= (-38 + 068 - 6 + 92 - 54 - 4)^6 \\ &:= (38 + 068 - 6 - 92 + 54 - 4)^6 \\ &:= (38 - 06 + 86 + 9 - 25 - 44)^6 \\ &:= (-3 + 80 - 68 + 6 + 92 - 5 - 44)^6 \\ &:= (3 - 80 + 6 + 86 + 92 - 5 - 44)^6 \\ &:= (38 - 068 + 69 - 25 + 44)^6 \\ &:= (-3 - 806 - 8 - 6 + 925 - 44)^6 \\ &:= (3 + 806 + 8 - 6 + 9 + 2544)^3 \\ &:= (3 - 80 + 686 - 9 + 2 - 544)^6 \\ \mathbf{38136631896} &:= (-381 + 3663 + 1 + 89 - 6)^3 \\ \mathbf{38167092496} &:= (381 + 67 - 09 + 2 + 4 - 9 + 6)^4 \\ &:= (381 + 6 + 7 + 09 + 24 + 9 + 6)^4 \\ &:= (381 + 6 - 7 + 09 - 2 + 49 + 6)^4 \\ &:= (381 + 6 + 7 - 09 + 2 + 49 + 6)^4 \\ &:= (3 - 81 + 6 + 7 + 09 + 2 + 496)^4 \\ &:= (-3 + 8 + 1 - 67 + 09 - 2 + 496)^4 \\ &:= (-38 - 16 - 7 + 09 - 2 + 496)^4 \\ &:= (-38 - 16 + 7 - 09 + 2 + 496)^4 \\ &:= (38 + 1 + 6 - 7 - 092 + 496)^4 \\ &:= (38 - 1 - 6 + 7 - 092 + 496)^4 \\ &:= (3 + 8 + 167 + 09 + 249 + 6)^4 \\ &:= (3 + 8 + 16 - 70 - 9 - 2 + 496)^4 \\ &:= (-3 - 8 + 16 - 70 + 9 + 2 + 496)^4 \\ &:= (-3 + 8 + 1 + 670 + 9 - 249 + 6)^4 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} &:= (3 - 8 - 1 - 6 + 709 - 249 - 6)^4 \\ &:= (-381 - 6 + 709 + 24 + 96)^4 \\ \mathbf{38306833811} &:= (-3 + 8 - 30 + 6 + 8 + 3381 + 1)^3 \\ &:= (3830 + 6 - 83 - 381 - 1)^3 \\ \mathbf{38340934848} &:= (38 + 3409 - 3 + 4 - 84 + 8)^3 \\ &:= (-3 + 8 + 3409 + 34 - 84 + 8)^3 \\ \mathbf{38443359375} &:= (38 + 4 - 4 + 3 + 3 - 5 - 9 - 3 - 7 - 5)^9 \\ &:= (38 - 4 + 4 + 3 + 3 - 5 - 9 - 3 - 7 - 5)^9 \\ &:= (38 + 4 - 4 + 3 - 3 - 5 - 9 + 3 - 7 - 5)^9 \\ &:= (38 - 4 + 4 + 3 - 3 - 5 - 9 + 3 - 7 - 5)^9 \\ &:= (38 + 4 - 4 - 3 + 3 - 5 - 9 + 3 - 7 - 5)^9 \\ &:= (38 - 4 + 4 - 3 + 3 - 5 - 9 + 3 - 7 - 5)^9 \\ &:= (38 - 4 - 4 + 3 - 3 - 5 - 9 - 3 + 7 - 5)^9 \\ &:= (38 - 4 - 4 - 3 + 3 - 5 - 9 - 3 + 7 - 5)^9 \\ &:= (38 - 4 - 4 - 3 - 3 - 5 - 9 + 3 + 7 - 5)^9 \\ &:= (38 - 4 - 4 - 3 - 3 + 5 - 9 - 3 - 7 + 5)^9 \\ &:= (3 + 8 + 4 - 4 + 33 - 5 - 9 - 3 - 7 - 5)^9 \\ &:= (3 + 8 - 4 + 4 + 33 - 5 - 9 - 3 - 7 - 5)^9 \\ &:= (-3 + 8 + 4 - 4 + 33 - 5 - 9 + 3 - 7 - 5)^9 \\ &:= (-3 + 8 - 4 + 4 + 33 - 5 - 9 + 3 - 7 - 5)^9 \\ &:= (3 - 8 + 4 - 4 + 33 + 5 - 9 + 3 - 7 - 5)^9 \\ &:= (3 - 8 - 4 + 4 + 33 + 5 - 9 + 3 - 7 - 5)^9 \\ &:= (3 - 8 - 4 - 4 + 33 - 5 + 9 + 3 - 7 - 5)^9 \\ &:= (-3 + 8 - 4 - 4 + 33 - 5 - 9 - 3 + 7 - 5)^9 \\ &:= (-3 - 8 + 4 + 4 + 33 - 5 - 9 - 3 + 7 - 5)^9 \\ &:= (3 - 8 - 4 - 4 + 33 + 5 - 9 - 3 + 7 - 5)^9 \\ &:= (-3 - 8 - 4 - 4 + 33 + 5 - 9 + 3 + 7 - 5)^9 \\ &:= (3 - 8 + 4 - 4 + 33 - 5 - 9 + 3 - 7 + 5)^9 \\ &:= (3 - 8 - 4 + 4 + 33 - 5 - 9 + 3 - 7 + 5)^9 \\ &:= (3 - 8 - 4 - 4 + 33 - 5 - 9 - 3 + 7 + 5)^9 \\ &:= (-3 - 8 - 4 - 4 + 33 - 5 - 9 + 3 + 7 + 5)^9 \\ &:= (3 + 8 + 4 + 4 - 33 + 5 + 9 + 3 + 7 + 5)^9 \\ &:= (-3 - 8 + 4 - 4 - 3 + 35 + 9 - 3 - 7 - 5)^9 \\ &:= (-3 - 8 - 4 + 4 - 3 + 35 + 9 - 3 - 7 - 5)^9 \\ &:= (3 - 8 + 4 - 4 + 3 + 35 - 9 + 3 - 7 - 5)^9 \\ &:= (3 - 8 - 4 + 4 + 3 + 35 - 9 + 3 - 7 - 5)^9 \\ &:= (3 - 8 - 4 - 4 + 3 + 35 - 9 - 3 + 7 - 5)^9 \\ &:= (3 - 8 - 4 - 4 - 3 + 35 - 9 + 3 + 7 - 5)^9 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} & := (-3-8-4-4+3+35-9+3+7-5)^9 & := (3-84-4+3-3+5+93+7-5)^9 \\ & := (-3+8-4-4-3+35-9-3-7+5)^9 & := (3-84-4-3+3+5+93+7-5)^9 \\ & := (-3-8+4+4-3+35-9-3-7+5)^9 & := (-3-84-4+3+3+5+93+7-5)^9 \\ & := (3+8-4-4-3-3-5-9+37-5)^9 & := (3-84+4+3+3-5+93-7+5)^9 \\ & := (3-8+4+4-3-3-5-9+37-5)^9 & := (3+84+4+3-3+5-93+7+5)^9 \\ & := (-3+8-4-4+3-3-5-9+37-5)^9 & := (3+84+4-3+3+5-93+7+5)^9 \\ & := (-3-8+4+4+3-3-5-9+37-5)^9 & := (-3+84+4+3+3+5-93+7+5)^9 \\ & := (-3+8-4-4-3+3-5-9+37-5)^9 & := (3-84-4+3-3-5+93+7+5)^9 \\ & := (-3-8+4+4-3+3-5-9+37-5)^9 & := (3-84-4-3+3-5+93+7+5)^9 \\ & := (3-8-4-4+3-3+5-9+37-5)^9 & := (-3-84-4+3+3-5+93+7+5)^9 \\ & := (3-8-4-4-3+3+5-9+37-5)^9 & := (-3+84-4-3-3-5-9-37-5)^9 \\ & := (-3-8-4-4+3+3+5-9+37-5)^9 & := (3+84+4+3+3+5-9-3-75)^9 \\ & := (3-8-4-4+3-3-5-9+37+5)^9 & := (3+84-4+3+3-5+9-3-75)^9 \\ & := (3-8-4-4-3+3-5-9+37+5)^9 & := (-3+84+4-3-3+5+9-3-75)^9 \\ & := (-3-8-4-4+3+3-5-9+37+5)^9 & := (3+84+4+3-3+5-9+3-75)^9 \\ & := (-38+44+3+3-5+9-3+7-5)^9 & := (3+84+4-3+3+5-9+3-75)^9 \\ & := (-38+44+3-3-5+9+3+7-5)^9 & := (-3+84+4+3+3+5-9+3-75)^9 \\ & := (-38+44-3+3-5+9+3+7-5)^9 & := (3+84-4+3-3-5+9+3-75)^9 \\ & := (-38+44+3-3+5+9-3-7+5)^9 & := (3+84-4-3+3-5+9+3-75)^9 \\ & := (-38+44-3+3+5+9-3-7+5)^9 & := (-3+84-4+3+3-5+9+3-75)^9 \\ & := (-38+44-3-3+5+9+3-7+5)^9 & := (3-84+4+3+3+5+9-3+75)^9 \\ & := (38-44+3+3+5+9+3-7+5)^9 & := (3-84+4+3-3+5+9+3+75)^9 \\ & := (-38+4+43+3-5+9-3+7-5)^9 & := (3-84+4-3+3+5+9+3+75)^9 \\ & := (38+4-43+3+5+9-3+7-5)^9 & := (-3-84+4+3+3+5+9+3+75)^9 \\ & := (-38+4+43-3-5+9+3+7-5)^9 & := (-3+8+44-33+5+9-3-7-5)^9 \\ & := (38+4-43-3+5+9+3+7-5)^9 & := (3-8+44-33-5+9+3+7-5)^9 \\ & := (-38+4+43-3+5+9-3-7+5)^9 & := (-3+8+44-33-5+9-3-7+5)^9 \\ & := (38+4-43+3-5+9-3+7+5)^9 & := (3-8+44-33+5+9-3-7+5)^9 \\ & := (-38-4+43+3+5-9+3+7+5)^9 & := (-3-8+44-33+5+9+3-7+5)^9 \\ & := (38+4-43-3-5+9+3+7+5)^9 & := (3+8-44+33+5+9+3-7+5)^9 \\ & := (-3+84-4-33-5-9-3-7-5)^9 & := (3-8+44+3-35+9-3+7-5)^9 \\ & := (-3+84-4-3-35-9-3-7-5)^9 & := (3-8+44-3-35+9+3+7-5)^9 \\ & := (3+84-4+3+3-59-3-7-5)^9 & := (-3-8+44+3-35+9+3+7-5)^9 \\ & := (3+84-4+3-3-59+3-7-5)^9 & := (-3+8+44-3-35+9-3-7+5)^9 \\ & := (3+84-4-3+3-59+3-7-5)^9 & := (3+8+44+3-35-9+3-7+5)^9 \\ & := (-3+84-4+3+3-59+3-7-5)^9 & := (3+8-44+3+35+9+3-7+5)^9 \\ & := (-3+84+4-3-3-59-3-7+5)^9 & := (3-8-44+3+3+59-3+7-5)^9 \\ & := (3-84+4+3+3+5+93-7-5)^9 & := (3-8-44+3-3+59+3+7-5)^9 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} &:= (3-8-44-3+3+59+3+7-5)^9 & &:= (3+8+4+43+3-5-9-37+5)^9 \\ &:= (-3-8-44+3+3+59+3+7-5)^9 & &:= (-3-8+4+43-3+5+9-37+5)^9 \\ &:= (3+8-44-3-3+59-3-7+5)^9 & &:= (3+8+4-43-3-5+9+37+5)^9 \\ &:= (-3+8-44+3-3+59-3-7+5)^9 & &:= (-3+8+4-43+3-5+9+37+5)^9 \\ &:= (-3+8-44-3+3+59-3-7+5)^9 & &:= (3-8+4-43+3+5+9+37+5)^9 \\ &:= (-3+8-44-3-3+59+3-7+5)^9 & &:= (-3-8+4-43-3+5-9-3+75)^9 \\ &:= (-3-8-44-3-3-5+93-7-5)^9 & &:= (-3-8-4-43-3-5+9-3+75)^9 \\ &:= (3+8+44+3+3+5-9-37-5)^9 & &:= (3-8-4-43+3-5-9+3+75)^9 \\ &:= (-3+8+44-3-3+5+9-37-5)^9 & &:= (38+4+4+33-59-3-7+5)^9 \\ &:= (3+8+44+3+3-5-9-37+5)^9 & &:= (-38+4-4-33+5+93-7-5)^9 \\ &:= (-3+8+44-3-3-5+9-37+5)^9 & &:= (-38-4+4-33+5+93-7-5)^9 \\ &:= (3-8+44-3-3+5+9-37+5)^9 & &:= (-38+4-4-33-5+93-7+5)^9 \\ &:= (-3-8+44+3-3+5+9-37+5)^9 & &:= (-38-4+4-33-5+93-7+5)^9 \\ &:= (-3-8+44-3+3+5+9-37+5)^9 & &:= (38+4-4+33-5-9-37-5)^9 \\ &:= (3-8-44+3+3-5-9-3+75)^9 & &:= (38-4+4+33-5-9-37-5)^9 \\ &:= (-3-8-44-3-3-5+9-3+75)^9 & &:= (38-4-4-33-5-9+37-5)^9 \\ &:= (3-8-44+3-3-5-9+3+75)^9 & &:= (-38-4-4+33+5-9+37-5)^9 \\ &:= (3-8-44-3+3-5-9+3+75)^9 & &:= (-38-4-4+33-5-9+37+5)^9 \\ &:= (-3-8-44+3+3-5-9+3+75)^9 & &:= (38+4+4+33+5+9-3-75)^9 \\ &:= (3+8-4+43-35+9+3-7-5)^9 & &:= (-38+4-4-33+5+9-3+75)^9 \\ &:= (3-8+4+43-35+9-3+7-5)^9 & &:= (-38-4+4-33+5+9-3+75)^9 \\ &:= (3+8+4-43+35+9-3+7-5)^9 & &:= (-38+4-4-3-35+93-7+5)^9 \\ &:= (-3-8+4+43-35+9+3+7-5)^9 & &:= (-38-4+4-3-35+93-7+5)^9 \\ &:= (-3+8+4-43+35+9+3+7-5)^9 & &:= (38-4-4-3-35-9+37-5)^9 \\ &:= (3+8+4+43-35-9+3-7+5)^9 & &:= (-38-4-4+3+35-9+37-5)^9 \\ &:= (3+8-4+43-35-9-3+7+5)^9 & &:= (38+4+4+3+35+9-3-75)^9 \\ &:= (-3+8-4+43-35-9+3+7+5)^9 & &:= (38+4+4-3+35+9+3-75)^9 \\ &:= (3-8+4-43+35+9+3+7+5)^9 & &:= (38+4-4-3-3-59+37+5)^9 \\ &:= (3-8-4-43+3+59+3+7-5)^9 & &:= (38-4+4-3-3-59+37+5)^9 \\ &:= (3+8-4-43-3+59-3-7+5)^9 & &:= (38+4-4+3-3-5-93+75)^9 \\ &:= (-3+8-4-43+3+59-3-7+5)^9 & &:= (38-4+4+3-3-5-93+75)^9 \\ &:= (-3+8-4-43-3+59+3-7+5)^9 & &:= (38+4-4-3+3-5-93+75)^9 \\ &:= (-3-8+4-43-3+59-3+7+5)^9 & &:= (38-4+4-3+3-5-93+75)^9 \\ &:= (-3-8-4-43-3-5+93-7-5)^9 & &:= (3-84+43+35+9-3+7+5)^9 \\ &:= (3+8+4+43+3+5-9-37-5)^9 & &:= (3+84-43-35-9+3+7+5)^9 \\ &:= (3+8-4+43+3-5+9-37-5)^9 & &:= (-3-84+43+35+9+3+7+5)^9 \\ &:= (3+8+4-43-3+5+9+37-5)^9 & &:= (3-84+43+3+59+3-7-5)^9 \\ &:= (-3+8+4-43+3+5+9+37-5)^9 & &:= (3-84+43-3+5+9+37+5)^9 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 &:= (-3 - 84 + 43 + 3 + 5 + 9 + 37 + 5)^9 \\
 &:= (3 + 8 + 4 - 4 + 3359 + 3 + 7 - 5)^3 \\
 &:= (3 + 8 - 4 + 4 + 3359 + 3 + 7 - 5)^3 \\
 &:= (3 - 8 + 4 - 4 + 33 + 59 + 3 - 75)^9 \\
 &:= (3 - 8 - 4 + 4 + 33 + 59 + 3 - 75)^9 \\
 &:= (-3 + 8 + 4 - 4 + 33 - 5 - 93 + 75)^9 \\
 &:= (-3 + 8 - 4 + 4 + 33 - 5 - 93 + 75)^9 \\
 &:= (3 - 8 + 4 - 4 + 33 + 5 - 93 + 75)^9 \\
 &:= (3 - 8 - 4 + 4 + 33 + 5 - 93 + 75)^9 \\
 &:= (3 - 8 + 4 - 4 + 3 + 35 - 93 + 75)^9 \\
 &:= (3 - 8 - 4 + 4 + 3 + 35 - 93 + 75)^9 \\
 &:= (384 - 4 + 3 - 359 + 3 - 7 - 5)^9 \\
 &:= (384 + 4 + 3 + 3 + 5 - 9 - 375)^9 \\
 &:= (384 - 4 + 3 + 3 - 5 + 9 - 375)^9 \\
 &:= (-384 + 4 + 3 + 3 + 5 + 9 + 375)^9 \\
 &:= (-38 - 44 + 33 + 59 + 3 + 7 - 5)^9 \\
 &:= (38 - 44 - 33 + 59 - 3 - 7 + 5)^9 \\
 &:= (38 + 44 + 33 + 5 - 93 - 7 - 5)^9 \\
 &:= (38 + 44 + 33 - 5 - 93 - 7 + 5)^9 \\
 &:= (-38 - 44 + 33 - 5 - 9 + 3 + 75)^9 \\
 &:= (38 + 44 + 3 + 35 - 93 - 7 - 5)^9 \\
 &:= (-38 + 44 + 3 - 35 + 9 + 37 - 5)^9 \\
 &:= (-38 + 44 - 3 + 35 + 9 - 37 + 5)^9 \\
 &:= (-38 - 44 + 3 + 3 + 59 + 37 - 5)^9 \\
 &:= (38 - 44 - 3 - 3 + 59 - 37 + 5)^9 \\
 &:= (38 + 4 - 43 - 3 - 59 - 3 + 75)^9 \\
 &:= (38 + 4 - 43 - 3 - 59 + 3 + 75)^9 \\
 &:= (38 + 4 - 43 + 3 - 5 + 93 - 75)^9 \\
 &:= (3 + 84 - 4 + 33 - 59 - 37 - 5)^9 \\
 &:= (-3 - 84 + 4 - 33 + 59 - 3 + 75)^9 \\
 &:= (384 - 433 + 59 + 3 + 7 - 5)^9 \\
 &:= (384 - 433 - 5 - 9 + 3 + 75)^9 \\
 &:= (38 + 4 + 4 + 335 + 9 - 375)^9
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 &:= (3 + 84 - 433 - 5 - 9 + 375)^9 \\
 &:= (3 - 84 + 43 + 35 + 93 - 75)^9 \\
 &:= (38 + 4 - 43 - 359 + 375)^9 \\
 \mathbf{38513670001} &:= (3 - 8 + 513 + 6 - 70 - 001)^4 \\
 &:= (-3 + 8 + 513 - 6 - 70 + 001)^4 \\
 \mathbf{38579489651} &:= (-3 + 85 + 7 + 9 + 4 + 8 + 9 + 6 + 5 + 1)^5 \\
 &:= (-3 + 8 + 5 + 7 + 9 + 4 + 89 + 6 + 5 + 1)^5 \\
 &:= (38 + 5 + 79 + 4 + 8 + 9 - 6 - 5 - 1)^5 \\
 &:= (38 - 5 + 79 + 4 + 8 + 9 - 6 + 5 - 1)^5 \\
 &:= (38 + 5 + 79 - 4 - 8 + 9 + 6 + 5 + 1)^5 \\
 &:= (38 + 5 + 7 + 94 + 8 - 9 - 6 - 5 - 1)^5 \\
 &:= (38 + 5 - 7 + 94 - 8 + 9 + 6 - 5 - 1)^5 \\
 &:= (38 - 5 + 7 + 94 + 8 - 9 - 6 + 5 - 1)^5 \\
 &:= (38 - 5 - 7 + 94 - 8 + 9 + 6 + 5 - 1)^5 \\
 &:= (38 + 5 - 7 + 94 + 8 - 9 + 6 - 5 + 1)^5 \\
 &:= (38 + 5 - 7 + 94 - 8 + 9 - 6 + 5 + 1)^5 \\
 &:= (38 - 5 - 7 + 94 + 8 - 9 + 6 + 5 + 1)^5 \\
 &:= (38 + 5 - 7 + 9 + 4 - 8 + 96 - 5 - 1)^5 \\
 &:= (38 - 5 - 7 + 9 + 4 - 8 + 96 + 5 - 1)^5 \\
 &:= (38 + 5 - 7 - 9 - 4 + 8 + 96 + 5 - 1)^5 \\
 &:= (38 - 5 - 7 + 9 - 4 + 8 + 96 - 5 + 1)^5 \\
 &:= (38 + 5 - 7 - 9 + 4 + 8 + 96 - 5 + 1)^5 \\
 &:= (38 + 5 + 7 - 9 - 4 - 8 + 96 + 5 + 1)^5 \\
 &:= (38 - 5 - 7 - 9 + 4 + 8 + 96 + 5 + 1)^5 \\
 &:= (3 + 85 + 7 + 9 + 48 - 9 - 6 - 5 - 1)^5 \\
 &:= (3 + 85 + 7 - 9 + 48 + 9 - 6 - 5 - 1)^5 \\
 &:= (-3 + 85 - 7 + 9 + 48 + 9 - 6 - 5 + 1)^5 \\
 &:= (3 + 85 - 7 + 9 + 48 - 9 + 6 - 5 + 1)^5 \\
 &:= (3 + 85 - 7 - 9 + 48 + 9 + 6 - 5 + 1)^5 \\
 &:= (-3 + 85 + 7 - 9 + 48 - 9 + 6 + 5 + 1)^5 \\
 &:= (-3 + 85 + 7 - 9 + 4 - 8 - 9 + 65 - 1)^5 \\
 &:= (3 + 85 - 7 - 9 - 4 + 8 - 9 + 65 - 1)^5 \\
 &:= (3 + 85 + 7 - 9 - 4 - 8 - 9 + 65 + 1)^5 \\
 &:= (-3 - 8 + 57 + 94 - 8 + 9 - 6 - 5 + 1)^5 \\
 &:= (3 - 8 + 57 + 94 - 8 - 9 + 6 - 5 + 1)^5 \\
 &:= (-3 + 8 + 57 - 9 - 4 - 8 + 96 - 5 - 1)^5 \\
 &:= (-3 - 8 + 57 - 9 - 4 + 8 + 96 - 5 - 1)^5 \\
 &:= (3 - 8 + 57 - 9 - 4 - 8 + 96 + 5 - 1)^5
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} &:= (3-8+57-9+4-8+96-5+1)^5 &:= (38-5-7-9+48+9+6+51)^5 \\ &:= (-3+8+57+9+4+8-9+6+51)^5 &:= (3+85+79+4+8+9-6-51)^5 \\ &:= (3+8+57+9-4-8+9+6+51)^5 &:= (3+85+7+94+8-9-6-51)^5 \\ &:= (3-8+57+9-4+8+9+6+51)^5 &:= (3+85-7+94-8+9+6-51)^5 \\ &:= (-3+8+57-9+4+8+9+6+51)^5 &:= (3+85+7+9-48+9+65+1)^5 \\ &:= (-3+8+5+79-4-8+9-6+51)^5 &:= (3+85+7+9+4+89-65-1)^5 \\ &:= (-3-8+5+79-4+8+9-6+51)^5 &:= (-3+85+7+9-4-8+96-51)^5 \\ &:= (3+8+5+79-4-8-9+6+51)^5 &:= (3+85-7+9+4-8+96-51)^5 \\ &:= (-3+8-5+79-4+8-9+6+51)^5 &:= (-3+8-57+94+89+6-5-1)^5 \\ &:= (3-8+5+79-4+8-9+6+51)^5 &:= (3-8-57+94+89+6+5-1)^5 \\ &:= (3-8-5+79+4-8+9+6+51)^5 &:= (-3+8-57+94+89-6+5+1)^5 \\ &:= (3+8+5-7+94-8-9-6+51)^5 &:= (3+8-57+94+8+9+65+1)^5 \\ &:= (-3+8-5-7+94+8-9-6+51)^5 &:= (3+8+57+9-48+96+5+1)^5 \\ &:= (3-8+5-7+94+8-9-6+51)^5 &:= (-3+8+5+79-48+96-5-1)^5 \\ &:= (-3-8-5+7+94-8+9-6+51)^5 &:= (-3+8-5+79-48+96+5-1)^5 \\ &:= (3-8-5+7+94-8-9+6+51)^5 &:= (3-8+5+79-48+96+5-1)^5 \\ &:= (-3-8+5+7+9+48+9+65-1)^5 &:= (3+8+5+79+4+89-6-51)^5 \\ &:= (-3+8+5+7+9+48-9+65+1)^5 &:= (-3+8-5-7+94+89+6-51)^5 \\ &:= (-3+8+5+7-9+48+9+65+1)^5 &:= (3-8+5-7+94+89+6-51)^5 \\ &:= (3+8-5-7+9+48+9+65+1)^5 &:= (3+8+5+7+9-48+96+51)^5 \\ &:= (-3-8-5+7-9-4+89+65-1)^5 &:= (38+57+94+8-9-6-51)^5 \\ &:= (3-8-5-7-9+4+89+65-1)^5 &:= (38-57+94+8-9+6+51)^5 \\ &:= (-3-8+5-7+9-4-8+96+51)^5 &:= (-38+57+9+48-9+65-1)^5 \\ &:= (3-8-5+7-9+4-8+96+51)^5 &:= (-38+57-9+48+9+65-1)^5 \\ &:= (38+57+9+48-9-6-5-1)^5 &:= (38+57+9-48+9+65+1)^5 \\ &:= (38+57-9+48+9-6-5-1)^5 &:= (38+57+9+4+89-65-1)^5 \\ &:= (-38+57+9+4+89+6+5-1)^5 &:= (38-57-9+4+89+65+1)^5 \\ &:= (38+57-9-4-8-9+65+1)^5 &:= (38-57-9+4+8+96+51)^5 \\ &:= (-38+5+79-4+89+6-5-1)^5 &:= (38+5+79-48-9+65+1)^5 \\ &:= (-38-5+79-4+89+6+5-1)^5 &:= (38-5+79-4+89-65-1)^5 \\ &:= (-38-5+79+4+89+6-5+1)^5 &:= (3-857+9+4+8+965-1)^5 \\ &:= (-38+5+79-4+89-6+5+1)^5 &:= (-3-85+79+48+96-5+1)^5 \\ &:= (-38+5+79+4+8+9+65-1)^5 &:= (3+85+79-4-89+6+51)^5 \\ &:= (-38+5-7+94+89-6-5-1)^5 &:= (3+85-7+94-89-6+51)^5 \\ &:= (-38-5-7+94+89-6+5-1)^5 &:= (-3+8+57+94-89+65-1)^5 \\ &:= (-38+5+7+94+8-9+65-1)^5 &:= (385-7-94-89-65+1)^5 \\ &:= (-38+5+7+9+48+96+5-1)^5 &:= (38-579+4+8+9+651)^5 \\ &:= (38-5-7+9+48-9+6+51)^5 &:= (38-5-794+896-5+1)^5 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 &:= (-38 + 5 - 794 - 8 + 965 + 1)^5 \\
 &:= (-38 + 5 - 7 + 9 - 489 + 651)^5 \\
 \mathbf{38648755341} &:= (3864 - 87 - 55 - 341)^3 \\
 \mathbf{38854881603} &:= (3885 - 488 - 1 - 6 - 03)^3 \\
 \mathbf{38862602496} &:= (-38 + 8 + 6 - 26 - 02 + 496)^4 \\
 &:= (3 - 88 - 62 + 602 + 4 - 9 - 6)^4 \\
 &:= (388 - 6 + 2 - 60 + 24 + 96)^4 \\
 \mathbf{38923752869} &:= (3892 + 3 + 7 - 528 + 6 + 9)^3 \\
 &:= (3 + 892 - 375 + 2869)^3 \\
 \mathbf{39061739457} &:= (3906 - 17 - 39 - 457)^3 \\
 \mathbf{39213900625} &:= (392 + 1 + 39 + 006 + 2 + 5)^4 \\
 &:= (39 + 2 + 1 + 390 + 06 + 2 + 5)^4 \\
 &:= (392 - 13 + 9 + 0062 - 5)^4 \\
 &:= (392 + 13 + 9 + 006 + 25)^4 \\
 &:= (39 - 2 - 1 + 390 - 06 + 25)^4 \\
 &:= (-392 + 1 + 3 + 900 - 62 - 5)^4 \\
 &:= (-39 - 2 - 139 + 00625)^4 \\
 \mathbf{39269330199} &:= (3 + 92 - 6 + 9 + 3301 + 9 - 9)^3 \\
 &:= (3 + 92 - 6 + 9 + 3301 - 9 + 9)^3 \\
 &:= (3 + 92 - 6 - 9 + 3301 + 9 + 9)^3 \\
 &:= (3 + 9 + 2 - 6 - 9 + 3301 + 99)^3 \\
 &:= (3 - 9 + 2 - 6 + 9 + 3301 + 99)^3 \\
 \mathbf{39373400808} &:= (3 + 9 - 3 - 7 + 3400 + 8 - 08)^3 \\
 &:= (-3 + 9 + 3 - 7 + 3400 + 8 - 08)^3 \\
 &:= (3 + 9 - 3 - 7 + 3400 - 8 + 08)^3 \\
 &:= (-3 + 9 + 3 - 7 + 3400 - 8 + 08)^3 \\
 &:= (39 - 37 + 3400 + 8 - 08)^3 \\
 &:= (39 - 37 + 3400 - 8 + 08)^3 \\
 \mathbf{39442883264} &:= (-3 + 9 + 44 + 2 + 88 + 3264)^3 \\
 &:= (-3 + 9 + 4 + 42 + 88 + 3264)^3 \\
 \mathbf{39512447416} &:= (-3 + 951 + 2447 + 4 + 1 + 6)^3 \\
 \mathbf{39567575056} &:= (395 + 67 - 5 - 7 - 5 - 05 + 6)^4 \\
 &:= (3 + 9 - 56 - 7 + 5 - 7 + 505 - 6)^4 \\
 &:= (3 - 9 - 56 + 7 - 5 + 7 + 505 - 6)^4 \\
 &:= (-3 + 9 + 5 + 6 - 75 - 7 + 505 + 6)^4 \\
 &:= (3 + 9 + 5 - 6 - 7 - 57 + 505 - 6)^4 \\
 &:= (-3 - 9 + 5 + 6 - 7 - 57 + 505 + 6)^4 \\
 &:= (395 - 67 + 57 + 50 + 5 + 6)^4
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 &:= (395 - 67 + 57 + 5 + 056)^4 \\
 &:= (395 - 67 + 5 + 7 + 50 + 56)^4 \\
 &:= (-39 + 56 - 75 - 7 + 505 + 6)^4 \\
 &:= (-3 - 95 + 675 - 75 - 056)^4 \\
 \mathbf{39922038025} &:= (-3992 + 203802 - 5)^2 \\
 \mathbf{39923636481} &:= (399 - 2 + 36 - 3 + 6 + 4 + 8 - 1)^4 \\
 &:= (399 - 2 + 36 + 3 + 6 - 4 + 8 + 1)^4 \\
 &:= (399 + 2 + 36 + 3 - 6 + 4 + 8 + 1)^4 \\
 &:= (399 - 2 - 3 + 6 + 36 + 4 + 8 - 1)^4 \\
 &:= (399 - 2 + 3 + 6 + 36 - 4 + 8 + 1)^4 \\
 &:= (399 + 2 + 3 - 6 + 36 + 4 + 8 + 1)^4 \\
 &:= (-39 + 9 + 2 - 3 + 6 - 3 - 6 + 481)^4 \\
 &:= (-39 + 9 + 2 + 3 - 6 + 3 - 6 + 481)^4 \\
 &:= (-39 + 9 + 2 - 3 - 6 - 3 + 6 + 481)^4 \\
 &:= (-39 - 9 + 2 + 3 + 6 - 3 + 6 + 481)^4 \\
 &:= (-39 - 9 + 2 - 3 + 6 + 3 + 6 + 481)^4 \\
 &:= (-3 + 9 + 9 - 2 + 363 + 64 + 8 - 1)^4 \\
 &:= (-3 + 9 + 9 - 2 + 363 - 6 - 4 + 81)^4 \\
 &:= (3 + 9 - 9 - 2 + 363 + 6 - 4 + 81)^4 \\
 &:= (3 - 9 + 9 - 2 + 363 + 6 - 4 + 81)^4 \\
 &:= (3 + 9 - 9 + 2 + 363 - 6 + 4 + 81)^4 \\
 &:= (3 - 9 + 9 + 2 + 363 - 6 + 4 + 81)^4 \\
 &:= (3 + 9 - 9 + 2 - 36 + 3 - 6 + 481)^4 \\
 &:= (3 - 9 + 9 + 2 - 36 + 3 - 6 + 481)^4 \\
 &:= (-3 + 9 - 9 + 2 - 36 - 3 + 6 + 481)^4 \\
 &:= (-3 - 9 + 9 + 2 - 36 - 3 + 6 + 481)^4 \\
 &:= (3 + 9 - 9 + 2 + 3 - 6 + 364 + 81)^4 \\
 &:= (3 - 9 + 9 + 2 + 3 - 6 + 364 + 81)^4 \\
 &:= (-3 + 9 - 9 + 2 - 3 + 6 + 364 + 81)^4 \\
 &:= (-3 - 9 + 9 + 2 - 3 + 6 + 364 + 81)^4 \\
 &:= (3 + 9 - 9 + 2 + 3 - 6 - 36 + 481)^4 \\
 &:= (3 - 9 + 9 + 2 + 3 - 6 - 36 + 481)^4 \\
 &:= (-3 + 9 - 9 + 2 - 3 + 6 - 36 + 481)^4 \\
 &:= (-3 - 9 + 9 + 2 - 3 + 6 - 36 + 481)^4 \\
 &:= (399 + 23 - 6 + 36 + 4 - 8 - 1)^4 \\
 &:= (399 - 2 - 36 + 3 + 6 - 4 + 81)^4 \\
 &:= (399 + 2 - 36 + 3 - 6 + 4 + 81)^4 \\
 &:= (399 - 2 + 3 + 6 - 36 - 4 + 81)^4
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 &:= (399 + 2 + 3 - 6 - 36 + 4 + 81)^4 \\
 &:= (-39 - 9 + 23 - 6 + 3 - 6 + 481)^4 \\
 &:= (39 - 9 + 2 + 3 - 63 - 6 + 481)^4 \\
 &:= (3 - 99 + 2 + 3 + 63 - 6 + 481)^4 \\
 &:= (-3 - 99 + 2 - 3 + 63 + 6 + 481)^4 \\
 &:= (3 - 9 - 9 + 23 - 6 + 364 + 81)^4 \\
 &:= (3 - 9 - 9 + 23 - 6 - 36 + 481)^4 \\
 &:= (399 - 2 + 36 - 3 - 64 + 81)^4 \\
 &:= (3 + 992 + 3 - 636 + 4 + 81)^4 \\
 \mathbf{39931550632} &:= (3993 + 1 - 550 + 6 - 32)^3 \\
 \mathbf{39992000400} &:= (39 - 99 + 200040 + 0)^2 \\
 \mathbf{39993200289} &:= (-399 + 93 + 200289)^2 \\
 \mathbf{40071907448} &:= (-4007 - 19 + 07448)^3 \\
 \mathbf{40074642432} &:= (40 + 07 + 46 + 42 - 4 + 3 - 2)^5 \\
 &:= (40 + 07 + 46 - 4 + 2 + 43 - 2)^5 \\
 &:= (40 + 07 + 46 - 4 - 2 + 43 + 2)^5 \\
 &:= (40 + 07 - 4 + 64 + 24 + 3 - 2)^5 \\
 &:= (40 - 07 - 4 + 64 - 2 + 43 - 2)^5 \\
 &:= (40 + 07 - 4 + 6 + 42 + 43 - 2)^5 \\
 &:= (40 + 07 + 4 - 6 + 42 + 43 + 2)^5 \\
 &:= (4 + 0074 - 6 + 4 + 24 + 32)^5 \\
 &:= (-4 + 007 + 46 + 42 + 43 - 2)^5 \\
 &:= (-40 + 074 + 64 - 2 + 4 + 32)^5 \\
 &:= (40 + 074 + 6 + 4 - 24 + 32)^5 \\
 &:= (-4 - 0074 + 642 - 432)^5 \\
 &:= (-400 - 74 + 642 - 4 - 32)^5 \\
 \mathbf{40177390625} &:= (-401 - 77 + 3906 + 2 - 5)^3 \\
 \mathbf{40282095616} &:= (402 + 8 - 2 - 09 + 56 - 1 - 6)^4 \\
 &:= (402 - 8 + 2 - 09 + 56 - 1 + 6)^4 \\
 &:= (402 + 8 + 2 + 09 + 5 + 6 + 16)^4 \\
 &:= (402 + 82 - 09 - 5 - 6 - 16)^4 \\
 &:= (402 + 8 - 20 + 9 + 56 - 1 - 6)^4 \\
 &:= (402 + 8 + 20 - 9 + 5 + 6 + 16)^4 \\
 &:= (402 + 8 - 2 + 095 - 61 + 6)^4 \\
 &:= (4 + 0282 + 095 + 61 + 6)^4 \\
 &:= (40 - 2 + 8 - 209 - 5 + 616)^4 \\
 \mathbf{40283058752} &:= (4 + 02830 + 587 + 5 + 2)^3 \\
 \mathbf{40318322589} &:= (4 + 03183 + 225 + 8 + 9)^3 \\
 &:= (4 + 03 + 1 + 832 + 2589)^3 \\
 \mathbf{40530337875} &:= (405 + 3033 + 7 - 8 - 7 + 5)^3 \\
 &:= (405 + 3033 - 7 - 8 + 7 + 5)^3 \\
 &:= (405 + 3033 - 78 + 75)^3 \\
 \mathbf{40642963201} &:= (4 + 06 + 429 + 6 + 3 + 2 - 01)^4 \\
 &:= (406 + 42 + 9 - 6 - 3 + 2 - 01)^4 \\
 &:= (406 + 42 - 9 + 6 + 3 + 2 - 01)^4 \\
 &:= (406 + 4 + 29 + 6 + 3 + 2 - 01)^4 \\
 &:= (406 + 4 + 2 + 9 + 6 + 3 + 20 - 1)^4 \\
 &:= (4 + 06 + 429 - 6 - 3 + 20 - 1)^4 \\
 &:= (4 - 06 + 429 + 6 - 3 + 20 - 1)^4 \\
 &:= (-4 + 06 + 429 - 6 + 3 + 20 + 1)^4 \\
 &:= (-4 - 06 + 429 + 6 + 3 + 20 + 1)^4 \\
 &:= (406 + 42 - 9 - 6 - 3 + 20 - 1)^4 \\
 &:= (406 + 4 + 29 - 6 - 3 + 20 - 1)^4 \\
 &:= (406 - 4 + 29 - 6 + 3 + 20 + 1)^4 \\
 &:= (-40 - 6 + 429 + 63 + 2 + 01)^4 \\
 &:= (40 - 6 - 4 + 2 + 96 + 320 + 1)^4 \\
 &:= (-4 + 0642 + 9 + 6 - 3 - 201)^4 \\
 &:= (-4 - 06 + 42 + 96 + 320 + 1)^4 \\
 \mathbf{40849752384} &:= (-4084 + 9 + 7523 - 8 + 4)^3 \\
 \mathbf{40885346125} &:= (-4 + 08 - 8 - 5 + 3461 - 2 - 5)^3 \\
 &:= (-4 - 08 + 8 - 5 + 3461 - 2 - 5)^3 \\
 &:= (-40 + 8 + 8 + 5 + 3461 - 2 + 5)^3 \\
 &:= (4 + 08 - 8 + 5 + 3461 - 25)^3 \\
 &:= (4 - 08 + 8 + 5 + 3461 - 25)^3 \\
 \mathbf{40956595623} &:= (4095 - 6 - 5 - 9 - 5 - 623)^3 \\
 &:= (4095 + 6 - 595 - 62 + 3)^3 \\
 \mathbf{41135081408} &:= (4 - 11 + 3508 - 1 - 40 - 8)^3 \\
 \mathbf{41206620664} &:= (4120 - 662 + 06 - 6 - 4)^3 \\
 &:= (4120 - 662 - 06 + 6 - 4)^3 \\
 &:= (4120 + 6 - 6 - 2 - 0664)^3 \\
 &:= (4120 - 6 + 6 - 2 - 0664)^3 \\
 \mathbf{41320319076} &:= (4 + 1 + 3 + 203190 + 76)^2 \\
 \mathbf{41349947912} &:= (41 + 3499 - 4 - 79 - 1 + 2)^3 \\
 &:= (41 + 3499 + 4 + 7 - 91 - 2)^3 \\
 &:= (-41 + 3499 - 4 + 7 + 9 - 12)^3 \\
 &:= (-41 + 3499 + 4 - 7 - 9 + 12)^3
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} &:= (4 + 1 + 3499 + 47 - 91 - 2)^3 \\ &:= (4 - 1 + 3499 - 47 - 9 + 12)^3 \\ \mathbf{41371966801} &:= (413 + 7 + 1 + 9 + 6 + 6 + 8 + 01)^4 \\ &:= (-4 + 1 + 371 + 96 - 6 - 8 + 01)^4 \\ &:= (413 - 71 + 96 + 6 + 8 - 01)^4 \\ &:= (-413 + 7 - 1 - 9 + 66 + 801)^4 \\ &:= (4 - 137 + 1 - 96 + 680 - 1)^4 \\ &:= (4 - 137 - 1 - 96 + 680 + 1)^4 \\ &:= (4 + 1 - 37 - 196 + 680 - 1)^4 \\ &:= (4 - 1 - 37 - 196 + 680 + 1)^4 \\ &:= (-413 + 719 + 66 + 80 - 1)^4 \\ \mathbf{41385831579} &:= (-4 - 1 + 3858 - 315 - 79)^3 \\ \mathbf{41421736000} &:= (-4 - 142 - 1 + 7 + 3600 + 0)^3 \\ \mathbf{41529573847} &:= (-415 + 29 - 5 + 7 + 3847)^3 \\ \mathbf{41601569625} &:= (4160 - 1 + 5 - 696 + 2 - 5)^3 \\ &:= (4160 - 1 - 5 - 696 + 2 + 5)^3 \\ \mathbf{41615795893} &:= (4 + 1 + 6 + 1 + 5 + 7 + 95 + 8 + 9 - 3)^5 \\ &:= (41 + 6 + 1 + 57 + 9 + 5 + 8 + 9 - 3)^5 \\ &:= (41 + 6 + 1 + 5 + 79 + 5 + 8 - 9 - 3)^5 \\ &:= (41 + 6 - 1 + 5 + 79 + 5 - 8 + 9 - 3)^5 \\ &:= (41 - 6 - 1 + 5 + 79 - 5 + 8 + 9 + 3)^5 \\ &:= (41 - 6 - 1 - 5 + 79 + 5 + 8 + 9 + 3)^5 \\ &:= (41 + 6 - 1 + 5 + 7 + 95 - 8 - 9 - 3)^5 \\ &:= (41 - 6 + 1 - 5 - 7 + 95 + 8 + 9 - 3)^5 \\ &:= (41 + 6 + 1 - 5 - 7 + 95 + 8 - 9 + 3)^5 \\ &:= (41 - 6 - 1 - 5 + 7 + 95 + 8 - 9 + 3)^5 \\ &:= (41 + 6 - 1 - 5 - 7 + 95 - 8 + 9 + 3)^5 \\ &:= (41 - 6 + 1 + 5 - 7 + 95 - 8 + 9 + 3)^5 \\ &:= (41 + 6 + 1 + 5 + 7 + 9 + 58 + 9 - 3)^5 \\ &:= (41 + 6 - 1 + 5 - 7 + 9 - 5 - 8 + 93)^5 \\ &:= (41 + 6 - 1 - 5 - 7 + 9 + 5 - 8 + 93)^5 \\ &:= (41 - 6 + 1 + 5 - 7 + 9 + 5 - 8 + 93)^5 \\ &:= (41 + 6 + 1 + 5 - 7 - 9 - 5 + 8 + 93)^5 \\ &:= (41 - 6 - 1 + 5 + 7 - 9 - 5 + 8 + 93)^5 \\ &:= (41 + 6 + 1 - 5 - 7 - 9 + 5 + 8 + 93)^5 \\ &:= (41 - 6 - 1 - 5 + 7 - 9 + 5 + 8 + 93)^5 \\ &:= (4 + 161 - 5 + 7 - 9 - 5 - 8 - 9 - 3)^5 \\ &:= (-4 + 161 - 5 - 7 - 9 - 5 + 8 - 9 + 3)^5 \\ &:= (4 + 16 + 1 + 5 + 7 + 9 + 5 + 89 - 3)^5 \\ &:= (4 + 1 + 61 + 57 + 9 + 5 + 8 - 9 - 3)^5 \\ &:= (4 - 1 + 61 + 57 + 9 + 5 - 8 + 9 - 3)^5 \\ &:= (-4 + 1 + 61 + 57 + 9 - 5 + 8 + 9 - 3)^5 \\ &:= (4 + 1 + 61 + 57 - 9 + 5 + 8 + 9 - 3)^5 \\ &:= (-4 + 1 + 61 + 57 + 9 + 5 - 8 + 9 + 3)^5 \\ &:= (4 - 1 + 61 + 5 + 79 + 5 - 8 - 9 - 3)^5 \\ &:= (-4 + 1 + 61 + 5 + 79 - 5 + 8 - 9 - 3)^5 \\ &:= (-4 + 1 + 61 - 5 + 79 + 5 + 8 - 9 - 3)^5 \\ &:= (4 + 1 + 61 - 5 + 79 - 5 - 8 + 9 - 3)^5 \\ &:= (-4 - 1 + 61 + 5 + 79 - 5 - 8 + 9 - 3)^5 \\ &:= (-4 - 1 + 61 - 5 + 79 + 5 - 8 + 9 - 3)^5 \\ &:= (-4 + 1 + 61 + 5 + 79 + 5 - 8 - 9 + 3)^5 \\ &:= (-4 - 1 + 61 - 5 + 7 + 95 - 8 - 9 - 3)^5 \\ &:= (4 - 1 + 61 - 5 - 7 + 95 - 8 - 9 + 3)^5 \\ &:= (4 + 1 + 61 + 5 + 7 + 9 + 58 - 9 - 3)^5 \\ &:= (4 + 1 + 61 + 5 + 7 - 9 + 58 + 9 - 3)^5 \\ &:= (-4 + 1 + 61 - 5 + 7 + 9 + 58 + 9 - 3)^5 \\ &:= (4 + 1 + 61 - 5 - 7 + 9 + 58 + 9 + 3)^5 \\ &:= (-4 - 1 + 61 + 5 - 7 + 9 + 58 + 9 + 3)^5 \\ &:= (4 - 1 + 61 + 5 - 7 - 9 - 5 - 8 + 93)^5 \\ &:= (-4 - 1 + 61 - 5 - 7 + 9 - 5 - 8 + 93)^5 \\ &:= (4 - 1 + 61 - 5 - 7 - 9 + 5 - 8 + 93)^5 \\ &:= (-4 + 1 + 61 - 5 - 7 - 9 - 5 + 8 + 93)^5 \\ &:= (4 + 1 + 6 + 15 + 7 + 9 + 5 + 89 - 3)^5 \\ &:= (-4 + 1 + 6 + 1 + 57 - 9 - 5 + 89 - 3)^5 \\ &:= (4 + 1 - 6 - 1 + 57 - 9 - 5 + 89 + 3)^5 \\ &:= (4 - 1 - 6 + 1 + 57 - 9 - 5 + 89 + 3)^5 \\ &:= (-4 - 1 - 6 - 1 + 57 - 9 + 5 + 89 + 3)^5 \\ &:= (-41 + 61 + 5 - 7 + 95 + 8 + 9 + 3)^5 \\ &:= (41 + 61 - 5 - 7 - 9 + 58 - 9 + 3)^5 \\ &:= (-41 + 61 + 5 - 7 + 9 + 5 + 8 + 93)^5 \\ &:= (41 - 6 + 15 - 7 + 9 - 5 + 89 - 3)^5 \\ &:= (41 + 6 + 15 - 7 - 9 - 5 + 89 + 3)^5 \\ &:= (41 - 6 - 15 + 7 + 9 + 5 + 89 + 3)^5 \\ &:= (-41 - 6 - 1 + 5 + 79 + 5 + 89 + 3)^5 \\ &:= (-41 + 6 - 1 - 5 - 7 + 95 + 89 - 3)^5 \\ &:= (-41 - 6 + 1 + 5 - 7 + 95 + 89 - 3)^5 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 &:= (4 - 16 + 157 - 9 - 5 + 8 - 9 + 3)^5 \\
 &:= (4 + 16 + 15 + 79 + 5 + 8 + 9 - 3)^5 \\
 &:= (4 + 16 + 15 + 7 + 95 + 8 - 9 - 3)^5 \\
 &:= (-4 + 16 + 15 + 7 + 95 - 8 + 9 + 3)^5 \\
 &:= (-4 + 16 + 15 + 7 + 9 + 5 - 8 + 93)^5 \\
 &:= (4 + 16 + 15 - 7 + 9 - 5 + 8 + 93)^5 \\
 &:= (-4 - 16 - 1 + 57 + 95 + 8 - 9 + 3)^5 \\
 &:= (4 + 16 + 1 + 57 + 9 + 58 - 9 - 3)^5 \\
 &:= (4 + 16 + 1 + 57 - 9 + 58 + 9 - 3)^5 \\
 &:= (4 - 16 - 1 + 57 + 9 - 5 - 8 + 93)^5 \\
 &:= (4 - 16 + 1 + 57 - 9 - 5 + 8 + 93)^5 \\
 &:= (-4 - 16 - 1 + 57 - 9 + 5 + 8 + 93)^5 \\
 &:= (-4 + 16 + 1 - 5 + 79 + 58 - 9 - 3)^5 \\
 &:= (4 - 16 + 1 - 5 + 79 + 58 + 9 + 3)^5 \\
 &:= (-4 - 16 - 1 + 5 + 79 + 58 + 9 + 3)^5 \\
 &:= (-4 - 16 - 1 - 5 + 79 - 5 - 8 + 93)^5 \\
 &:= (4 - 16 + 1 - 5 + 7 - 9 + 58 + 93)^5 \\
 &:= (-4 - 16 - 1 + 5 + 7 - 9 + 58 + 93)^5 \\
 &:= (4 + 1 - 61 - 5 + 7 + 95 + 89 + 3)^5 \\
 &:= (-4 - 1 - 61 + 5 + 7 + 95 + 89 + 3)^5 \\
 &:= (4 + 1 - 6 - 15 + 79 + 58 + 9 + 3)^5 \\
 &:= (-4 - 1 - 6 - 15 + 79 - 5 - 8 + 93)^5 \\
 &:= (4 + 1 - 6 - 15 + 7 - 9 + 58 + 93)^5 \\
 &:= (4 + 1 + 6 - 1 - 57 + 95 - 8 + 93)^5 \\
 &:= (4 - 1 + 6 + 1 - 57 + 95 - 8 + 93)^5 \\
 &:= (41 - 61 + 57 + 9 - 5 + 89 + 3)^5 \\
 &:= (41 + 61 - 57 - 9 + 5 + 89 + 3)^5 \\
 &:= (41 + 6 + 157 + 9 + 5 + 8 - 93)^5 \\
 &:= (-41 + 6 + 15 - 7 + 9 + 58 + 93)^5 \\
 &:= (41 + 6 + 1 - 57 - 9 + 58 + 93)^5 \\
 &:= (-4 + 161 + 57 - 95 + 8 + 9 - 3)^5 \\
 &:= (-4 + 161 + 57 + 9 - 5 + 8 - 93)^5 \\
 &:= (4 + 161 + 57 - 9 + 5 + 8 - 93)^5 \\
 &:= (4 + 161 - 5 - 79 + 58 - 9 + 3)^5 \\
 &:= (4 + 161 - 5 + 79 - 5 - 8 - 93)^5 \\
 &:= (4 + 161 + 5 + 7 - 9 + 58 - 93)^5 \\
 &:= (-4 + 161 - 5 + 7 + 9 + 58 - 93)^5 \\
 &:= (4 - 16 - 15 + 79 - 5 + 89 - 3)^5
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 &:= (4 + 1 + 61 + 57 + 95 + 8 - 93)^5 \\
 &:= (-4 - 1 - 61 + 57 - 9 + 58 + 93)^5 \\
 &:= (4 + 1 + 61 - 5 - 79 + 58 + 93)^5 \\
 &:= (-4 - 1 + 61 + 5 - 79 + 58 + 93)^5 \\
 &:= (41 + 61 + 57 + 9 + 58 - 93)^5 \\
 &:= (-41 - 61 + 5 + 79 + 58 + 93)^5 \\
 &:= (4 + 16 + 157 - 9 + 58 - 93)^5 \\
 &:= (4 + 16 + 15 - 795 + 893)^5 \\
 &**41637598696** := (4163 - 7 + 5 + 9 - 8 - 696)^3 \\
 &**41740124416** := (4 + 1 + 7 + 4 - 01 + 2 + 441 - 6)^4 \\
 &:= (4 - 1 + 7 + 4 + 01 + 2 + 441 - 6)^4 \\
 &:= (4 + 1 + 7 - 4 - 01 - 2 + 441 + 6)^4 \\
 &:= (-4 + 1 + 7 + 4 - 01 - 2 + 441 + 6)^4 \\
 &:= (4 - 1 + 7 - 4 + 01 - 2 + 441 + 6)^4 \\
 &:= (-4 - 1 + 7 + 4 + 01 - 2 + 441 + 6)^4 \\
 &:= (4 + 1 - 7 + 4 + 01 + 2 + 441 + 6)^4 \\
 &:= (41 + 7 + 401 + 2 + 4 + 4 - 1 - 6)^4 \\
 &:= (41 + 7 + 401 - 2 + 4 - 4 - 1 + 6)^4 \\
 &:= (41 + 7 + 401 - 2 - 4 + 4 - 1 + 6)^4 \\
 &:= (41 - 7 + 401 + 2 + 4 + 4 + 1 + 6)^4 \\
 &:= (4 + 1 + 7 + 401 + 2 + 44 - 1 - 6)^4 \\
 &:= (4 - 1 + 7 + 401 + 2 + 44 + 1 - 6)^4 \\
 &:= (-4 + 1 + 7 + 401 - 2 + 44 - 1 + 6)^4 \\
 &:= (-4 - 1 + 7 + 401 - 2 + 44 + 1 + 6)^4 \\
 &:= (4 + 1 - 7 + 401 + 2 + 44 + 1 + 6)^4 \\
 &:= (4 - 1 + 7 + 401 + 2 + 4 + 41 - 6)^4 \\
 &:= (4 - 1 + 7 + 401 - 2 - 4 + 41 + 6)^4 \\
 &:= (-4 - 1 + 7 + 401 - 2 + 4 + 41 + 6)^4 \\
 &:= (4 + 1 - 7 + 401 + 2 + 4 + 41 + 6)^4 \\
 &:= (417 + 40 - 12 + 4 - 4 + 1 + 6)^4 \\
 &:= (417 + 40 - 12 - 4 + 4 + 1 + 6)^4 \\
 &:= (417 + 40 + 1 + 2 + 4 + 4 - 16)^4 \\
 &:= (417 - 4 - 012 + 44 + 1 + 6)^4 \\
 &:= (417 + 4 - 012 - 4 + 41 + 6)^4 \\
 &:= (417 - 4 - 012 + 4 + 41 + 6)^4 \\
 &:= (417 + 4 + 01 + 2 + 44 - 16)^4 \\
 &:= (-41 + 74 + 01 - 2 + 4 + 416)^4 \\
 &:= (41 + 7 - 40 - 1 - 2 + 441 + 6)^4
 \end{aligned}$$

$:= (-41 + 7 + 40 + 1 - 2 + 441 + 6)^4$	$:= (-4 - 2 + 1107 + 33 - 681)^4$
$:= (41 + 7 + 4 - 012 - 4 + 416)^4$	42180533641 $:= (42 + 1 + 8 + 05 + 3 + 3 - 6 + 4 - 1)^6$
$:= (41 + 7 - 4 - 012 + 4 + 416)^4$	$:= (42 + 1 + 8 + 05 - 3 - 3 + 6 + 4 - 1)^6$
$:= (4 + 17 - 4 - 012 + 441 + 6)^4$	$:= (42 - 1 + 8 - 05 + 3 + 3 + 6 + 4 - 1)^6$
$:= (-4 + 17 + 4 - 012 + 441 + 6)^4$	$:= (42 + 1 + 8 + 05 + 3 - 3 + 6 - 4 + 1)^6$
$:= (4 + 1 + 7 + 40 - 12 - 4 + 416)^4$	$:= (42 + 1 + 8 + 05 - 3 + 3 + 6 - 4 + 1)^6$
$:= (-4 - 1 - 7 + 40 + 12 - 4 + 416)^4$	$:= (42 - 1 + 8 + 05 + 3 + 3 - 6 + 4 + 1)^6$
$:= (-4 + 1 + 7 + 40 - 12 + 4 + 416)^4$	$:= (42 - 1 + 8 + 05 - 3 - 3 + 6 + 4 + 1)^6$
$:= (417 + 40 - 1 - 24 + 4 + 16)^4$	$:= (4 - 2 - 1 + 80 - 5 - 3 - 3 - 6 - 4 - 1)^6$
$:= (4 + 17 + 401 + 2 + 44 - 16)^4$	$:= (-4 - 2 + 1 + 80 - 5 + 3 - 3 - 6 - 4 - 1)^6$
$:= (4 + 17 + 40 - 1 - 24 + 416)^4$	$:= (-4 - 2 + 1 + 80 - 5 - 3 + 3 - 6 - 4 - 1)^6$
$:= (-41 - 7 - 40 + 124 + 416)^4$	$:= (-4 - 2 - 1 + 80 - 5 - 3 - 3 - 6 + 4 - 1)^6$
$:= (41 + 7 - 4012 + 4416)^4$	$:= (-4 + 2 + 1 + 80 - 5 - 3 - 3 - 6 - 4 + 1)^6$
41745810709 $:= (4174 - 5 + 8 + 1 - 0709)^3$	$:= (-4 - 2 - 1 + 80 - 5 + 3 - 3 - 6 - 4 + 1)^6$
41999034176 $:= (4199 - 903 + 4 + 176)^3$	$:= (-4 - 2 - 1 + 80 - 5 - 3 + 3 - 6 - 4 + 1)^6$
$:= (4 + 199 - 903 + 4176)^3$	$:= (-4 + 2 + 1 + 8 - 05 - 3 - 3 + 64 - 1)^6$
42035292333 $:= (-4 - 20 + 3529 + 2 - 33 + 3)^3$	$:= (4 + 2 - 1 - 8 + 05 - 3 - 3 + 64 - 1)^6$
$:= (-4 - 20 + 3529 + 2 + 3 - 33)^3$	$:= (-4 - 2 - 1 + 8 - 05 + 3 - 3 + 64 - 1)^6$
$:= (-42 + 03529 + 23 - 33)^3$	$:= (-4 + 2 + 1 - 8 + 05 + 3 - 3 + 64 - 1)^6$
42050833969 $:= (4 + 205083 - 39 + 6 + 9)^2$	$:= (-4 - 2 - 1 + 8 - 05 - 3 + 3 + 64 - 1)^6$
42051244096 $:= (-4 + 205124 + 40 - 96)^2$	$:= (-4 + 2 + 1 - 8 + 05 - 3 + 3 + 64 - 1)^6$
42082009321 $:= (4208 + 200932 - 1)^2$	$:= (4 - 2 + 1 - 8 - 05 + 3 + 3 + 64 - 1)^6$
42110733681 $:= (421 + 10 + 7 + 3 - 3 + 6 + 8 + 1)^4$	$:= (-4 - 2 - 1 - 8 + 05 + 3 + 3 + 64 - 1)^6$
$:= (421 + 10 + 7 - 3 + 3 + 6 + 8 + 1)^4$	$:= (-4 + 2 - 1 + 8 - 05 - 3 - 3 + 64 + 1)^6$
$:= (421 + 1 + 07 - 3 + 36 - 8 - 1)^4$	$:= (4 - 2 + 1 - 8 + 05 - 3 - 3 + 64 + 1)^6$
$:= (421 - 1 - 07 - 3 + 36 + 8 - 1)^4$	$:= (4 + 2 + 1 - 8 - 05 + 3 - 3 + 64 + 1)^6$
$:= (421 - 1 + 07 - 3 + 36 - 8 + 1)^4$	$:= (-4 + 2 - 1 - 8 + 05 + 3 - 3 + 64 + 1)^6$
$:= (-4 - 211 - 07 - 3 - 3 + 681)^4$	$:= (4 + 2 + 1 - 8 - 05 - 3 + 3 + 64 + 1)^6$
$:= (4 - 2 + 11 + 073 + 368 - 1)^4$	$:= (-4 + 2 - 1 - 8 + 05 - 3 + 3 + 64 + 1)^6$
$:= (4 - 2 + 1 + 107 + 336 + 8 - 1)^4$	$:= (4 - 2 - 1 - 8 - 05 + 3 + 3 + 64 + 1)^6$
$:= (4 - 2 - 1 + 107 + 336 + 8 + 1)^4$	$:= (4 + 2 - 1 + 8 + 05 + 3 + 3 - 6 + 41)^6$
$:= (4 - 2 + 1 + 10 + 73 + 368 - 1)^4$	$:= (4 + 2 - 1 + 8 + 05 - 3 - 3 + 6 + 41)^6$
$:= (4 - 2 - 1 + 10 + 73 + 368 + 1)^4$	$:= (-4 + 2 + 1 + 8 + 05 + 3 - 3 + 6 + 41)^6$
$:= (421 + 107 - 3 - 3 - 68 - 1)^4$	$:= (-4 + 2 + 1 + 8 + 05 - 3 + 3 + 6 + 41)^6$
$:= (421 + 107 + 3 - 3 + 6 - 81)^4$	$:= (4 - 2 + 1 + 8 - 05 + 3 + 3 + 6 + 41)^6$
$:= (421 + 107 - 3 + 3 + 6 - 81)^4$	$:= (-4 - 2 - 1 + 8 + 05 + 3 + 3 + 6 + 41)^6$
$:= (-4 + 21 + 107 + 336 - 8 + 1)^4$	$:= (-42 + 1 + 80 + 5 + 3 + 3 + 6 + 4 - 1)^6$
$:= (-42 - 110 - 73 - 3 + 681)^4$	$:= (-42 - 1 + 80 + 5 + 3 + 3 + 6 + 4 + 1)^6$

$$\begin{aligned}
 &:= (42 + 1 - 8 - 05 - 3 - 3 - 6 + 41)^6 \\
 &:= (4 - 21 + 80 - 5 + 3 - 3 + 6 - 4 - 1)^6 \\
 &:= (4 - 21 + 80 - 5 - 3 + 3 + 6 - 4 - 1)^6 \\
 &:= (4 - 21 + 80 + 5 - 3 - 3 - 6 + 4 - 1)^6 \\
 &:= (-4 - 21 + 80 - 5 + 3 - 3 + 6 + 4 - 1)^6 \\
 &:= (-4 - 21 + 80 - 5 - 3 + 3 + 6 + 4 - 1)^6 \\
 &:= (4 - 21 + 80 + 5 + 3 - 3 - 6 - 4 + 1)^6 \\
 &:= (4 - 21 + 80 + 5 - 3 + 3 - 6 - 4 + 1)^6 \\
 &:= (-4 - 21 + 80 - 5 + 3 + 3 + 6 - 4 + 1)^6 \\
 &:= (-4 - 21 + 80 + 5 + 3 - 3 - 6 + 4 + 1)^6 \\
 &:= (-4 - 21 + 80 + 5 - 3 + 3 - 6 + 4 + 1)^6 \\
 &:= (4 - 21 + 8 + 05 + 3 - 3 + 64 - 1)^6 \\
 &:= (4 - 21 + 8 + 05 - 3 + 3 + 64 - 1)^6 \\
 &:= (-4 - 21 + 8 + 05 + 3 + 3 + 64 + 1)^6 \\
 &:= (-4 + 21 + 8 + 05 - 3 - 3 - 6 + 41)^6 \\
 &:= (4 + 21 - 8 - 05 + 3 - 3 + 6 + 41)^6 \\
 &:= (4 + 21 - 8 - 05 - 3 + 3 + 6 + 41)^6 \\
 &:= (4 - 2 + 18 + 053 - 3 - 6 - 4 - 1)^6 \\
 &:= (-4 - 2 + 18 + 053 - 3 - 6 + 4 - 1)^6 \\
 &:= (-4 - 2 + 18 + 053 + 3 - 6 - 4 + 1)^6 \\
 &:= (4 - 2 + 18 + 05 + 33 + 6 - 4 - 1)^6 \\
 &:= (4 + 2 + 18 + 05 + 33 - 6 + 4 - 1)^6 \\
 &:= (-4 - 2 + 18 + 05 + 33 + 6 + 4 - 1)^6 \\
 &:= (4 - 2 + 18 - 05 + 33 + 6 + 4 + 1)^6 \\
 &:= (4 - 2 + 18 + 05 + 3 + 36 - 4 - 1)^6 \\
 &:= (-4 - 2 + 18 + 05 + 3 + 36 + 4 - 1)^6 \\
 &:= (4 + 2 + 18 + 05 - 3 + 36 - 4 + 1)^6 \\
 &:= (-4 + 2 + 18 + 05 - 3 + 36 + 4 + 1)^6 \\
 &:= (4 - 2 + 18 - 05 + 3 + 36 + 4 + 1)^6 \\
 &:= (4 - 2 + 1 + 80 + 5 + 3 + 3 + 6 - 41)^6 \\
 &:= (42 - 18 + 05 + 33 - 6 + 4 - 1)^6 \\
 &:= (42 - 18 + 05 - 3 + 36 - 4 + 1)^6 \\
 &:= (42 + 1 + 80 - 5 + 3 + 3 - 64 - 1)^6 \\
 &:= (42 + 1 + 80 + 5 - 3 - 3 - 64 + 1)^6 \\
 &:= (42 - 1 + 80 - 5 + 3 + 3 - 64 + 1)^6 \\
 &:= (-42 + 1 + 8 + 053 + 36 + 4 - 1)^6 \\
 &:= (-42 - 1 + 8 + 053 + 36 + 4 + 1)^6 \\
 &:= (4 + 21 + 80 - 5 + 3 + 3 - 6 - 41)^6
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 &:= (4 + 21 + 80 - 5 - 3 - 3 + 6 - 41)^6 \\
 &:= (4 - 21 - 8 + 053 + 36 - 4 - 1)^6 \\
 &:= (-4 - 21 - 8 + 053 + 36 + 4 - 1)^6 \\
 &:= (4 + 2 + 18 + 05 - 33 + 64 - 1)^6 \\
 &:= (4 - 2 - 18 - 05 + 33 + 6 + 41)^6 \\
 &:= (-4 + 2 - 18 + 05 - 3 + 36 + 41)^6 \\
 &:= (4 - 2 - 18 - 05 + 3 + 36 + 41)^6 \\
 &:= (4 - 2 - 1 + 80 - 53 + 36 - 4 - 1)^6 \\
 &:= (-4 - 2 - 1 + 80 - 53 + 36 + 4 - 1)^6 \\
 &:= (-4 + 2 + 1 + 80 - 53 + 36 - 4 + 1)^6 \\
 &:= (4 - 2 + 1 + 8 + 053 + 36 - 41)^6 \\
 &:= (-4 - 2 - 1 + 8 + 053 - 36 + 41)^6 \\
 &:= (-42 - 18 + 053 + 3 + 64 - 1)^6 \\
 &:= (42 - 18 + 05 - 33 + 64 - 1)^6 \\
 &:= (-42 + 1 + 80 + 53 - 36 + 4 - 1)^6 \\
 &:= (-42 - 1 + 80 + 53 - 36 + 4 + 1)^6 \\
 &:= (42 + 1 - 8 - 053 + 36 + 41)^6 \\
 &:= (-4 - 2 + 180 - 53 + 3 - 64 - 1)^6 \\
 &:= (-4 + 2 + 180 - 53 - 3 - 64 + 1)^6 \\
 &:= (4 - 2 + 1 + 80 + 53 - 36 - 41)^6 \\
 &:= (-42 + 180 - 5 + 3 - 36 - 41)^6 \\
 &:= (42 + 1 + 80 - 5 + 3364 - 1)^3 \\
 &:= (42 - 1 + 80 - 5 + 3364 + 1)^3 \\
 &:= (-42 + 1 - 8 - 0533 + 641)^6 \\
 &:= (-42 + 4 + 3551 - 027 + 2)^3 \\
 &:= (4 - 2 + 4 + 8 - 3 - 8 - 05 + 456)^4 \\
 &:= (4 - 2 + 4 - 8 - 3 + 8 - 05 + 456)^4 \\
 &:= (-4 - 2 - 4 + 8 - 3 + 8 - 05 + 456)^4 \\
 &:= (4 - 2 + 4 - 8 + 3 - 8 + 05 + 456)^4 \\
 &:= (-4 - 2 - 4 + 8 + 3 - 8 + 05 + 456)^4 \\
 &:= (-4 - 2 - 4 - 8 + 3 + 8 + 05 + 456)^4 \\
 &:= (424 - 8 + 38 + 05 - 4 + 5 - 6)^4 \\
 &:= (424 - 8 + 38 - 05 + 4 - 5 + 6)^4 \\
 &:= (424 - 8 + 3 - 8 + 054 - 5 - 6)^4 \\
 &:= (42 + 4 + 8 + 380 + 5 + 4 + 5 + 6)^4 \\
 &:= (4 - 24 + 8 - 3 + 8 + 05 + 456)^4 \\
 &:= (4 + 2 + 483 + 8 - 054 + 5 + 6)^4 \\
 &:= (4 + 2 + 48 + 380 + 5 + 4 + 5 + 6)^4
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} &:= (4 - 2 + 4 - 83 - 8 + 0545 - 6)^4 & &:= (-4 + 2 + 6 + 18 + 4 + 4 - 2 - 9 + 7 + 7)^7 \\ &:= (-4 - 2 - 4 - 83 + 8 + 0545 - 6)^4 & &:= (4 - 2 + 6 + 18 + 4 - 4 + 2 - 9 + 7 + 7)^7 \\ &:= (-4 + 2 - 4 - 83 - 8 + 0545 + 6)^4 & &:= (4 - 2 + 6 + 18 - 4 + 4 + 2 - 9 + 7 + 7)^7 \\ &:= (4 + 2 + 4 + 8 + 380 + 5 + 45 + 6)^4 & &:= (4 + 2 - 6 + 18 + 4 + 4 + 2 - 9 + 7 + 7)^7 \\ &:= (4 - 2 + 4 - 8 - 3 - 80 + 545 - 6)^4 & &:= (-4 - 2 + 6 + 18 + 4 + 4 + 2 - 9 + 7 + 7)^7 \\ &:= (-4 - 2 - 4 + 8 - 3 - 80 + 545 - 6)^4 & &:= (42 + 6 + 18 - 4 - 4 - 2 - 9 - 7 - 7)^7 \\ &:= (-4 + 2 - 4 - 8 - 3 - 80 + 545 + 6)^4 & &:= (42 - 6 + 18 + 4 - 4 + 2 - 9 - 7 - 7)^7 \\ &:= (424 + 8 - 3 + 80 - 54 + 5 - 6)^4 & &:= (42 - 6 + 18 - 4 + 4 + 2 - 9 - 7 - 7)^7 \\ &:= (424 + 8 - 3 + 80 + 5 - 4 - 56)^4 & &:= (42 - 6 - 18 + 4 + 4 - 2 + 9 + 7 - 7)^7 \\ &:= (-42 - 48 - 3 + 8 + 0545 - 6)^4 & &:= (42 + 6 - 18 - 4 - 4 + 2 + 9 + 7 - 7)^7 \\ &:= (42 - 4 - 8 + 380 + 5 + 45 - 6)^4 & &:= (42 - 6 - 18 + 4 + 4 - 2 + 9 - 7 + 7)^7 \\ &:= (-4 + 24 + 8 + 380 - 5 + 45 + 6)^4 & &:= (42 + 6 - 18 - 4 - 4 + 2 + 9 - 7 + 7)^7 \\ &:= (-4 - 24 + 8 + 3 - 80 + 545 + 6)^4 & &:= (42 + 6 - 18 + 4 - 4 - 2 - 9 + 7 + 7)^7 \\ &:= (-4 + 2 + 483 - 80 + 54 + 5 - 6)^4 & &:= (42 + 6 - 18 - 4 + 4 - 2 - 9 + 7 + 7)^7 \\ &:= (-4 - 2 + 483 - 80 + 5 - 4 + 56)^4 & &:= (42 - 6 - 18 + 4 + 4 + 2 - 9 + 7 + 7)^7 \\ &:= (4 - 2 + 4 - 83 + 80 - 5 + 456)^4 & &:= (-42 - 6 + 1 - 8 + 4 - 4 - 2 + 97 - 7)^7 \\ &:= (-4 - 2 - 4 + 83 - 80 + 5 + 456)^4 & &:= (-42 - 6 + 1 - 8 - 4 + 4 - 2 + 97 - 7)^7 \\ &:= (-42 - 48 + 3 + 80 + 5 + 456)^4 & &:= (-42 - 6 - 1 + 8 + 4 + 4 - 2 - 9 + 77)^7 \\ &:= (-4 - 24 - 8 + 380 + 54 + 56)^4 & &:= (-42 + 6 - 1 + 8 - 4 - 4 + 2 - 9 + 77)^7 \\ \mathbf{42618264157} &:= (-42 - 618 + 2 - 6 + 4157)^3 & &:= (-42 + 6 - 1 - 8 + 4 + 4 + 2 - 9 + 77)^7 \\ \mathbf{42618442977} &:= (4 - 2 + 6 + 18 + 4 - 4 - 2 + 9 + 7 - 7)^7 & &:= (-42 + 6 + 1 - 8 - 4 - 4 - 2 + 9 + 77)^7 \\ &:= (4 - 2 + 6 + 18 - 4 + 4 - 2 + 9 + 7 - 7)^7 & &:= (-42 - 6 + 1 - 8 + 4 - 4 + 2 + 9 + 77)^7 \\ &:= (4 + 2 - 6 + 18 + 4 + 4 - 2 + 9 + 7 - 7)^7 & &:= (-42 - 6 + 1 - 8 - 4 + 4 + 2 + 9 + 77)^7 \\ &:= (-4 - 2 + 6 + 18 + 4 + 4 - 2 + 9 + 7 - 7)^7 & &:= (4 + 26 + 18 - 4 - 4 - 2 + 9 - 7 - 7)^7 \\ &:= (4 + 2 + 6 + 18 - 4 - 4 + 2 + 9 + 7 - 7)^7 & &:= (-4 + 26 + 18 + 4 - 4 - 2 + 9 - 7 - 7)^7 \\ &:= (-4 + 2 + 6 + 18 + 4 - 4 + 2 + 9 + 7 - 7)^7 & &:= (-4 + 26 + 18 - 4 + 4 - 2 + 9 - 7 - 7)^7 \\ &:= (-4 + 2 + 6 + 18 - 4 + 4 + 2 + 9 + 7 - 7)^7 & &:= (4 + 26 + 18 - 4 - 4 + 2 - 9 + 7 - 7)^7 \\ &:= (4 - 2 - 6 + 18 + 4 + 4 + 2 + 9 + 7 - 7)^7 & &:= (-4 + 26 + 18 + 4 - 4 + 2 - 9 + 7 - 7)^7 \\ &:= (4 - 2 + 6 + 18 + 4 - 4 - 2 + 9 - 7 + 7)^7 & &:= (-4 + 26 + 18 - 4 + 4 + 2 - 9 + 7 - 7)^7 \\ &:= (4 - 2 + 6 + 18 - 4 + 4 - 2 + 9 - 7 + 7)^7 & &:= (4 + 26 + 18 - 4 - 4 + 2 - 9 - 7 + 7)^7 \\ &:= (4 + 2 - 6 + 18 + 4 + 4 - 2 + 9 - 7 + 7)^7 & &:= (-4 + 26 + 18 + 4 - 4 + 2 - 9 - 7 + 7)^7 \\ &:= (-4 - 2 + 6 + 18 + 4 + 4 - 2 + 9 - 7 + 7)^7 & &:= (-4 + 26 + 18 - 4 + 4 + 2 - 9 - 7 + 7)^7 \\ &:= (4 + 2 + 6 + 18 - 4 - 4 + 2 + 9 - 7 + 7)^7 & &:= (4 + 26 - 18 + 4 - 4 - 2 + 9 + 7 + 7)^7 \\ &:= (-4 + 2 + 6 + 18 + 4 - 4 + 2 + 9 - 7 + 7)^7 & &:= (4 + 26 - 18 - 4 + 4 - 2 + 9 + 7 + 7)^7 \\ &:= (-4 + 2 + 6 + 18 - 4 + 4 + 2 + 9 - 7 + 7)^7 & &:= (-4 + 26 - 18 + 4 + 4 - 2 + 9 + 7 + 7)^7 \\ &:= (4 - 2 - 6 + 18 + 4 + 4 + 2 + 9 - 7 + 7)^7 & &:= (4 - 26 + 1 - 8 - 4 - 4 + 2 - 9 + 77)^7 \\ &:= (4 + 2 + 6 + 18 + 4 - 4 - 2 - 9 + 7 + 7)^7 & &:= (-4 - 26 + 1 - 8 + 4 - 4 + 2 - 9 + 77)^7 \\ &:= (4 + 2 + 6 + 18 - 4 + 4 - 2 - 9 + 7 + 7)^7 & &:= (-4 - 26 + 1 - 8 - 4 + 4 + 2 - 9 + 77)^7 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} &:= (4+2-61+8-4-4-2+97-7)^7 & &:= (-4-2+6+18+4-4+29-7-7)^7 \\ &:= (-4+2-61+8+4-4-2+97-7)^7 & &:= (4+2-6+18-4+4+29-7-7)^7 \\ &:= (-4+2-61+8-4+4-2+97-7)^7 & &:= (-4-2+6+18-4+4+29-7-7)^7 \\ &:= (4+2-61-8+4+4-2+97-7)^7 & &:= (-4+2-6+18+4+4+29-7-7)^7 \\ &:= (4-2-61+8-4-4+2+97-7)^7 & &:= (4-2+6-18+4-4+29+7+7)^7 \\ &:= (-4-2-61+8+4-4+2+97-7)^7 & &:= (4-2+6-18-4+4+29+7+7)^7 \\ &:= (-4-2-61+8-4+4+2+97-7)^7 & &:= (4+2-6-18+4+4+29+7+7)^7 \\ &:= (4-2-61-8+4+4+2+97-7)^7 & &:= (-4-2+6-18+4+4+29+7+7)^7 \\ &:= (4-2-61+8+4-4-2+9+77)^7 & &:= (4+2+6-1-84+4-2+97+7)^7 \\ &:= (4-2-61+8-4+4-2+9+77)^7 & &:= (4-2+6-1-84+4+2+97+7)^7 \\ &:= (-4-2-61+8+4+4-2+9+77)^7 & &:= (4+2+6-1+84+4+2+9-77)^7 \\ &:= (4+2-61+8-4-4+2+9+77)^7 & &:= (4-2-6+1-8-44-2+97-7)^7 \\ &:= (-4+2-61+8+4-4+2+9+77)^7 & &:= (-4+2-6+1-8-44+2+97-7)^7 \\ &:= (-4+2-61+8-4+4+2+9+77)^7 & &:= (-4+2+6-1+8-44-2-9+77)^7 \\ &:= (4+2-61-8+4+4+2+9+77)^7 & &:= (4+2-6-1+8-44+2-9+77)^7 \\ &:= (4-2-6+18+44-2-9-7-7)^7 & &:= (-4-2+6-1+8-44+2-9+77)^7 \\ &:= (-4+2-6+18+44+2-9-7-7)^7 & &:= (4+2-6+1-8-44-2+9+77)^7 \\ &:= (4+2-6-18+44-2+9+7-7)^7 & &:= (-4-2+6+1-8-44-2+9+77)^7 \\ &:= (-4-2+6-18+44-2+9+7-7)^7 & &:= (4-2-6+1-8-44+2+9+77)^7 \\ &:= (4-2-6-18+44+2+9+7-7)^7 & &:= (4-2-6+1-8-4-42+97-7)^7 \\ &:= (4+2-6-18+44-2+9-7+7)^7 & &:= (-4-2-6+1-8+4-42+97-7)^7 \\ &:= (-4-2+6-18+44-2+9-7+7)^7 & &:= (-4+2+6-1+8-4-42-9+77)^7 \\ &:= (4-2-6-18+44+2+9-7+7)^7 & &:= (4+2+6-1-8+4-42-9+77)^7 \\ &:= (-4+2+6-18+44-2-9+7+7)^7 & &:= (4-2-6-1+8+4-42-9+77)^7 \\ &:= (4+2-6-18+44+2-9+7+7)^7 & &:= (4+2-6+1-8-4-42+9+77)^7 \\ &:= (-4-2+6-18+44+2-9+7+7)^7 & &:= (-4-2+6+1-8-4-42+9+77)^7 \\ &:= (4+2-6+18-4+42-9-7-7)^7 & &:= (-4+2-6+1-8+4-42+9+77)^7 \\ &:= (-4-2+6+18-4+42-9-7-7)^7 & &:= (4+2-6+1-8-4-4-29+77)^7 \\ &:= (-4+2-6+18+4+42-9-7-7)^7 & &:= (-4-2+6+1-8-4-4-29+77)^7 \\ &:= (-4+2+6-18-4+42+9+7-7)^7 & &:= (-4+2-6+1-8+4-4-29+77)^7 \\ &:= (4-2-6-18+4+42+9+7-7)^7 & &:= (-4+2-6+1-8-4+4-29+77)^7 \\ &:= (-4+2+6-18-4+42+9-7+7)^7 & &:= (42+61+8-4-4-2+9-77)^7 \\ &:= (4-2-6-18+4+42+9-7+7)^7 & &:= (42+61-8+4+4-2+9-77)^7 \\ &:= (4-2+6-18-4+42-9+7+7)^7 & &:= (-42+6+18+44-2+9+7-7)^7 \\ &:= (4+2-6-18+4+42-9+7+7)^7 & &:= (42+6+18-44+2+9+7-7)^7 \\ &:= (-4-2+6-18+4+42-9+7+7)^7 & &:= (-42+6+18+44-2+9-7+7)^7 \\ &:= (4-2+6+18-4-4+29-7-7)^7 & &:= (42+6+18-44+2+9-7+7)^7 \\ &:= (4+2-6+18+4-4+29-7-7)^7 & &:= (-42+6+18+44+2-9+7+7)^7 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} &:= (42 - 6 - 18 - 4 + 42 - 9 - 7 - 7)^7 &:= (-4 + 26 + 1 + 84 - 4 - 2 + 9 - 77)^7 \\ &:= (42 + 6 + 18 + 4 - 42 - 9 + 7 + 7)^7 &:= (4 + 26 - 1 - 84 + 4 - 2 + 9 + 77)^7 \\ &:= (-42 + 6 + 18 + 4 + 42 - 9 + 7 + 7)^7 &:= (4 - 26 - 1 + 8 - 44 + 2 + 97 - 7)^7 \\ &:= (42 - 6 - 18 + 4 - 4 + 29 - 7 - 7)^7 &:= (4 - 26 + 1 - 8 - 44 + 2 + 97 + 7)^7 \\ &:= (42 - 6 - 18 - 4 + 4 + 29 - 7 - 7)^7 &:= (4 - 26 - 1 + 8 + 4 - 42 + 9 + 77)^7 \\ &:= (42 - 6 + 18 + 4 + 4 - 29 + 7 - 7)^7 &:= (4 - 26 - 1 + 8 + 4 - 4 - 29 + 77)^7 \\ &:= (42 - 6 + 18 + 4 + 4 - 29 - 7 + 7)^7 &:= (4 - 26 - 1 + 8 - 4 + 4 - 29 + 77)^7 \\ &:= (-42 + 6 + 18 + 4 + 4 + 29 + 7 + 7)^7 &:= (-4 - 26 - 1 + 8 + 4 + 4 - 29 + 77)^7 \\ &:= (42 + 6 - 1 + 84 + 4 + 2 - 97 - 7)^7 &:= (-4 + 2 + 61 + 84 - 4 - 2 - 97 - 7)^7 \\ &:= (42 - 6 + 1 + 84 + 4 - 2 - 97 + 7)^7 &:= (-4 - 2 + 61 + 84 - 4 + 2 - 97 - 7)^7 \\ &:= (42 - 6 + 1 + 84 - 4 + 2 - 9 - 77)^7 &:= (-4 - 2 + 61 - 84 - 4 - 2 - 9 + 77)^7 \\ &:= (42 + 6 - 1 - 84 + 4 - 2 - 9 + 77)^7 &:= (4 + 2 + 61 - 8 + 44 - 2 + 9 - 77)^7 \\ &:= (42 - 6 + 1 - 84 - 4 - 2 + 9 + 77)^7 &:= (4 - 2 + 61 - 8 + 44 + 2 + 9 - 77)^7 \\ &:= (-42 + 6 - 1 + 8 - 44 + 2 + 97 + 7)^7 &:= (-4 - 2 + 61 + 8 - 4 + 42 + 9 - 77)^7 \\ &:= (42 + 6 - 1 + 8 + 44 + 2 + 9 - 77)^7 &:= (4 - 2 + 61 - 8 + 4 + 42 + 9 - 77)^7 \\ &:= (42 + 6 - 1 + 8 + 4 + 42 + 9 - 77)^7 &:= (-4 + 2 - 6 - 18 + 44 + 29 - 7 - 7)^7 \\ &:= (4 - 26 + 18 + 44 - 2 + 9 - 7 - 7)^7 &:= (4 + 2 - 6 + 18 + 44 - 29 + 7 - 7)^7 \\ &:= (4 - 26 + 18 + 44 + 2 - 9 + 7 - 7)^7 &:= (-4 - 2 + 6 + 18 + 44 - 29 + 7 - 7)^7 \\ &:= (4 - 26 + 18 + 44 + 2 - 9 - 7 + 7)^7 &:= (4 + 2 - 6 + 18 + 44 - 29 - 7 + 7)^7 \\ &:= (-4 + 26 - 18 - 4 + 42 - 9 + 7 - 7)^7 &:= (-4 - 2 + 6 + 18 + 44 - 29 - 7 + 7)^7 \\ &:= (4 - 26 + 18 + 4 + 42 - 9 + 7 - 7)^7 &:= (4 + 2 + 6 - 1 + 84 + 42 - 97 - 7)^7 \\ &:= (-4 + 26 - 18 - 4 + 42 - 9 - 7 + 7)^7 &:= (4 - 2 - 6 + 1 + 84 + 42 - 97 + 7)^7 \\ &:= (4 - 26 + 18 + 4 + 42 - 9 - 7 + 7)^7 &:= (-4 + 2 - 6 + 1 + 84 + 42 - 9 - 77)^7 \\ &:= (4 + 26 + 18 + 4 - 42 + 9 + 7 + 7)^7 &:= (4 - 2 + 6 - 1 - 84 + 42 - 9 + 77)^7 \\ &:= (4 + 26 - 18 - 4 - 4 + 29 + 7 - 7)^7 &:= (-4 - 2 - 6 + 1 - 84 + 42 + 9 + 77)^7 \\ &:= (-4 + 26 - 18 + 4 - 4 + 29 + 7 - 7)^7 &:= (4 + 2 - 6 + 1 + 84 - 4 + 29 - 77)^7 \\ &:= (-4 + 26 - 18 - 4 + 4 + 29 + 7 - 7)^7 &:= (-4 - 2 + 6 + 1 + 84 - 4 + 29 - 77)^7 \\ &:= (4 - 26 + 18 + 4 + 4 + 29 + 7 - 7)^7 &:= (-4 + 2 - 6 + 1 + 84 + 4 + 29 - 77)^7 \\ &:= (4 + 26 - 18 - 4 - 4 + 29 - 7 + 7)^7 &:= (4 - 2 + 6 - 1 - 84 + 4 + 29 + 77)^7 \\ &:= (-4 + 26 - 18 + 4 - 4 + 29 - 7 + 7)^7 &:= (-42 + 61 - 84 - 4 - 2 + 97 + 7)^7 \\ &:= (-4 + 26 - 18 - 4 + 4 + 29 - 7 + 7)^7 &:= (-42 + 61 + 84 - 4 + 2 + 9 - 77)^7 \\ &:= (4 - 26 + 18 + 4 + 4 + 29 - 7 + 7)^7 &:= (42 + 61 - 8 + 44 - 2 - 97 - 7)^7 \\ &:= (4 + 26 + 18 + 4 - 4 - 29 + 7 + 7)^7 &:= (42 - 61 + 8 - 44 - 2 + 97 - 7)^7 \\ &:= (4 + 26 + 18 - 4 + 4 - 29 + 7 + 7)^7 &:= (-42 + 61 - 8 - 44 - 2 - 9 + 77)^7 \\ &:= (-4 + 26 + 18 + 4 + 4 - 29 + 7 + 7)^7 &:= (-42 - 61 + 8 + 44 - 2 + 9 + 77)^7 \\ &:= (4 + 26 - 1 - 84 - 4 + 2 + 97 - 7)^7 &:= (42 - 61 + 8 - 44 + 2 + 9 + 77)^7 \\ &:= (-4 + 26 - 1 - 84 + 4 + 2 + 97 - 7)^7 &:= (42 - 61 + 8 - 4 - 42 + 97 - 7)^7 \\ &:= (4 + 26 - 1 + 84 + 4 + 2 - 9 - 77)^7 &:= (-42 - 61 + 8 - 4 + 42 + 97 - 7)^7 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 & := (-42 + 61 - 8 - 4 - 42 - 9 + 77)^7 \\
 & := (42 - 6 - 18 + 44 - 29 + 7 - 7)^7 \\
 & := (42 - 6 - 18 + 44 - 29 - 7 + 7)^7 \\
 & := (-42 + 6 - 18 + 44 + 29 + 7 + 7)^7 \\
 & := (42 - 6 + 1 - 8 - 44 - 29 + 77)^7 \\
 & := (-42 + 6 - 1 + 8 - 44 + 29 + 77)^7 \\
 & := (4 - 261 + 8 - 4 - 4 + 297 - 7)^7 \\
 & := (-4 - 261 + 8 + 4 - 4 + 297 - 7)^7 \\
 & := (-4 - 261 + 8 - 4 + 4 + 297 - 7)^7 \\
 & := (4 - 261 - 8 + 4 + 4 + 297 - 7)^7 \\
 & := (4 + 26 + 18 - 44 + 29 + 7 - 7)^7 \\
 & := (4 - 26 - 18 + 44 + 29 + 7 - 7)^7 \\
 & := (4 + 26 + 18 - 44 + 29 - 7 + 7)^7 \\
 & := (4 - 26 - 18 + 44 + 29 - 7 + 7)^7 \\
 & := (-4 + 26 - 18 + 44 - 29 + 7 + 7)^7 \\
 & := (-4 - 26 + 1 - 84 + 42 + 97 + 7)^7 \\
 & := (4 + 26 - 1 + 8 + 44 + 29 - 77)^7 \\
 & := (-4 + 26 - 1 + 8 - 44 - 29 + 77)^7 \\
 & := (4 - 26 + 1 - 8 - 44 + 29 + 77)^7 \\
 & := (-4 - 2 + 61 - 84 - 42 + 97 + 7)^7 \\
 & := (-4 + 2 + 61 + 84 - 42 + 9 - 77)^7 \\
 & := (-4 + 2 + 61 + 84 - 4 - 29 - 77)^7 \\
 & := (-4 - 2 - 61 + 8 + 44 - 29 + 77)^7 \\
 & := (426 + 18 + 4 - 429 + 7 + 7)^7 \\
 & := (426 - 1 - 84 - 4 - 297 - 7)^7 \\
 & := (-42 - 61 + 84 + 4 - 29 + 77)^7 \\
 & := (42 + 61 - 8 + 44 - 29 - 77)^7 \\
 & := (-4 + 261 + 84 - 4 - 297 - 7)^7 \\
 & := (-4261 + 8 - 4 + 4297 - 7)^7 \\
 \mathbf{42654877784} & := (4265 - 4 + 8 + 7 - 778 - 4)^3 \\
 & := (4265 + 4 - 8 + 7 - 778 + 4)^3 \\
 \mathbf{42764844473} & := (4276 - 4 - 844 - 4 + 73)^3 \\
 \mathbf{42838260499} & := (-42 + 838 + 2604 + 99)^3 \\
 \mathbf{42859350625} & := (428 - 5 + 9 - 3 - 5 + 06 + 25)^4 \\
 & := (4 - 2 + 85 + 9 + 350 + 6 - 2 + 5)^4 \\
 & := (-4 + 2 + 85 + 9 + 350 + 6 + 2 + 5)^4 \\
 & := (4 + 2 + 8 - 59 - 3 + 506 + 2 - 5)^4 \\
 & := (-4 - 2 + 8 - 59 + 3 + 506 - 2 + 5)^4 \\
 & := (4 + 2 - 8 - 59 + 3 + 506 + 2 + 5)^4 \\
 & := (428 + 59 - 35 + 06 + 2 - 5)^4 \\
 & := (42 + 85 - 9 + 350 - 6 - 2 - 5)^4 \\
 & := (42 + 8 - 5 - 93 + 506 + 2 - 5)^4 \\
 & := (42 - 8 + 5 - 93 + 506 - 2 + 5)^4 \\
 & := (42 - 8 + 5 + 9 + 350 + 62 - 5)^4 \\
 & := (42 - 8 - 5 + 9 + 350 + 62 + 5)^4 \\
 & := (-4 + 28 + 5 + 9 + 350 + 62 + 5)^4 \\
 & := (-4 + 2 + 85 - 9 + 350 + 6 + 25)^4 \\
 & := (-4 - 2 - 8 - 59 - 3 + 506 + 25)^4 \\
 & := (428 + 59 + 35 - 062 - 5)^4 \\
 & := (-428 + 5 + 935 - 062 + 5)^4 \\
 & := (42 + 85 + 9 + 350 - 6 - 25)^4 \\
 & := (-4 + 285 + 93 + 50 + 6 + 25)^4 \\
 & := (-4 - 28 + 5 - 93 - 50 + 625)^4 \\
 & := (428 - 593 - 5 + 0625)^4 \\
 & := (-42 - 85 - 93 + 50 + 625)^4 \\
 \mathbf{42948542008} & := (4 + 2948 + 542 + 008)^3 \\
 \mathbf{42985344527} & := (-4 + 2985 + 3 - 4 - 4 + 527)^3 \\
 \mathbf{43059012625} & := (4 - 30 + 5 + 901 + 2625)^3 \\
 \mathbf{43132764843} & := (4313 + 27 + 6 + 4 - 843)^3 \\
 & := (4313 - 27 + 64 - 843)^3 \\
 \mathbf{43169672512} & := (4 + 31 - 6 + 967 + 2512)^3 \\
 \mathbf{43204003424} & := (43 + 2 + 040 + 03 + 42 + 4)^5 \\
 & := (43 + 20 + 40 + 03 + 4 + 24)^5 \\
 & := (4 + 32 + 040 + 034 + 24)^5 \\
 & := (432 + 040 - 0342 + 4)^5 \\
 & := (-4 - 320 + 400 + 34 + 24)^5 \\
 \mathbf{43237380096} & := (432 + 3 + 7 + 3 + 8 + 009 - 6)^4 \\
 & := (432 - 3 + 7 - 3 + 8 + 009 + 6)^4 \\
 & := (-4 - 3 + 2 + 373 - 8 + 0096)^4 \\
 & := (43 + 23 + 7 + 380 + 09 - 6)^4 \\
 & := (4 - 323 - 7 - 3 + 800 - 9 - 6)^4 \\
 & := (4 + 32 + 37 + 380 + 09 - 6)^4 \\
 & := (432 + 37 + 3 + 80 - 096)^4 \\
 \mathbf{43243551000} & := (-43 - 2 + 4 + 3551 + 000)^3 \\
 \mathbf{43280521831} & := (4 + 3280 + 5 + 218 + 3 + 1)^3 \\
 \mathbf{43317513728} & := (-43 + 3 - 175 - 1 + 3728)^3
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 43354526697 &:= (4 - 3 + 3545 - 2 + 66 - 97)^3 \\ 43428615875 &:= (4 + 3428 + 6 - 1 - 5 + 8 + 75)^3 \\ &:= (4 + 3428 - 6 + 1 + 5 + 8 + 75)^3 \\ &:= (-4 + 3428 - 6 + 15 + 87 - 5)^3 \\ &:= (4 + 3428 + 6 - 15 + 87 + 5)^3 \\ &:= (4342 - 8 + 61 - 5 - 875)^3 \\ 43465692096 &:= (4 + 3465 - 69 + 20 + 96)^3 \\ 43470165025 &:= (43470 + 165025)^2 \\ 43502789413 &:= (-4 + 3502 - 7 + 8 + 9 - 4 + 13)^3 \\ 43502789413 &:= (4 + 3502 - 7 - 8 + 9 + 4 + 13)^3 \\ 43539907832 &:= (4 + 3539 - 9 - 07 - 8 - 3 + 2)^3 \\ &:= (-4 + 3539 - 90 + 78 - 3 - 2)^3 \\ &:= (4353 - 9 - 907 + 83 - 2)^3 \\ 43577047359 &:= (-4 + 3577 - 047 - 3 + 5 - 9)^3 \\ 43617904801 &:= (4 - 3 - 6 - 1 - 7 - 9 + 0480 - 1)^4 \\ &:= (-4 + 3 - 6 + 1 - 7 - 9 + 0480 - 1)^4 \\ &:= (-4 + 3 - 6 - 1 - 7 - 9 + 0480 + 1)^4 \\ &:= (436 + 17 + 9 + 04 - 8 - 01)^4 \\ &:= (436 + 17 - 9 + 04 + 8 + 01)^4 \\ &:= (-43 + 6 - 1 + 7 + 9 + 0480 - 1)^4 \\ &:= (4 + 361 + 79 + 04 + 8 + 01)^4 \\ &:= (4 + 361 + 7 + 90 + 4 - 8 - 01)^4 \\ &:= (-4 + 361 + 7 + 90 - 4 + 8 - 01)^4 \\ &:= (436 - 17 - 9 + 048 - 01)^4 \\ &:= (436 + 1 + 7 + 90 + 4 - 80 - 1)^4 \\ &:= (436 - 1 + 7 + 90 + 4 - 80 + 1)^4 \\ &:= (4 - 36 + 17 - 9 + 0480 + 1)^4 \\ &:= (4 + 3 + 617 - 90 + 4 - 80 - 1)^4 \\ &:= (-436 - 1 + 7 + 90 - 4 + 801)^4 \\ &:= (43 + 6 + 17 - 90 + 480 + 1)^4 \\ 43688592648 &:= (4 - 3 + 6 + 8 + 859 + 2648)^3 \\ 43763061824 &:= (437 - 6 + 3061 + 8 + 24)^3 \\ 43800328125 &:= (-4 + 3800 + 3 - 281 + 2 + 5)^3 \\ 43912253952 &:= (-439 + 12 - 2 + 5 + 3952)^3 \\ 44000935696 &:= (-4 + 400 - 09 + 3 + 5 + 69 - 6)^4 \\ 44102100025 &:= (4 + 4 - 10 + 210002 + 5)^2 \\ 44211654656 &:= (-4 + 4211 - 654 - 6 - 5 - 6)^3 \\ 44211654656 &:= (-4 + 4211 - 6 - 5 - 4 - 656)^3 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 44286716872 &:= (4428 - 6 - 7 + 1 - 6 - 872)^3 \\ 44324279819 &:= (-4 + 4324 - 2 - 798 + 19)^3 \\ 44361864000 &:= (-44 + 3618 + 6 - 40 + 00)^3 \\ 44386483761 &:= (4 + 438 + 6 + 4 - 8 + 3 + 7 + 6 - 1)^4 \\ &:= (-4 + 438 + 6 - 4 + 8 + 3 + 7 + 6 - 1)^4 \\ &:= (4 + 438 + 6 + 4 + 8 - 3 + 7 - 6 + 1)^4 \\ &:= (4 + 438 - 6 + 4 + 8 - 3 + 7 + 6 + 1)^4 \\ &:= (443 - 8 + 6 - 4 - 8 + 37 - 6 - 1)^4 \\ &:= (443 - 8 - 6 - 4 - 8 + 37 + 6 - 1)^4 \\ &:= (44 + 386 + 4 + 8 + 3 + 7 + 6 + 1)^4 \\ &:= (-4 + 438 - 6 + 48 - 3 - 7 - 6 - 1)^4 \\ &:= (4 + 4 + 386 + 48 + 3 + 7 + 6 + 1)^4 \\ &:= (4 + 4 + 386 - 4 + 83 - 7 - 6 - 1)^4 \\ &:= (4 - 4 + 386 + 4 + 83 - 7 - 6 - 1)^4 \\ &:= (-4 + 4 + 386 + 4 + 83 - 7 - 6 - 1)^4 \\ &:= (-4 - 4 + 386 - 4 + 83 + 7 - 6 + 1)^4 \\ &:= (4 + 4 - 38 + 6 + 483 + 7 - 6 - 1)^4 \\ &:= (4 + 4 - 38 - 6 + 483 + 7 + 6 - 1)^4 \\ &:= (4 + 4 - 38 + 6 + 483 - 7 + 6 + 1)^4 \\ &:= (443 + 86 - 4 + 8 + 3 - 76 - 1)^4 \\ &:= (443 - 8 + 64 - 8 - 37 + 6 - 1)^4 \\ &:= (443 + 8 - 64 - 8 + 3 + 76 + 1)^4 \\ &:= (443 - 8 - 64 + 8 + 3 + 76 + 1)^4 \\ &:= (443 - 8 + 6 + 48 - 37 + 6 + 1)^4 \\ &:= (443 - 8 - 6 - 48 + 3 + 76 - 1)^4 \\ &:= (443 + 8 + 6 - 4 + 83 - 76 - 1)^4 \\ &:= (-44 + 38 - 6 + 483 - 7 - 6 + 1)^4 \\ &:= (44 + 38 + 6 + 4 - 8 + 376 - 1)^4 \\ &:= (4 + 438 - 64 + 83 - 7 + 6 - 1)^4 \\ &:= (4 + 438 - 6 - 48 + 3 + 7 + 61)^4 \\ &:= (4 + 438 + 6 - 4 + 83 - 7 - 61)^4 \\ &:= (-4 + 438 + 6 + 4 + 83 - 7 - 61)^4 \\ &:= (-4 + 43 + 8 + 6 + 483 - 76 - 1)^4 \\ &:= (4 - 4 + 38 + 6 + 483 - 7 - 61)^4 \\ &:= (-4 + 4 + 38 + 6 + 483 - 7 - 61)^4 \\ &:= (-4 - 4 + 38 + 6 + 48 + 376 - 1)^4 \\ &:= (-443 + 864 + 8 + 37 - 6 - 1)^4 \\ &:= (443 - 86 - 4 + 8 + 37 + 61)^4 \end{aligned}$$

$:= (-443 + 8 + 64 + 837 - 6 - 1)^4$	$:= (-45 + 1 - 6 + 517 - 5 + 4 - 4 - 1)^4$
44437096088 $:= (44 + 4370 - 960 + 88)^3$	$:= (-45 + 1 - 6 + 517 - 5 - 4 + 4 - 1)^4$
44840334375 $:= (44 + 84 + 03 + 3 - 4 + 3 + 7 - 5)^5$	$:= (-45 - 1 - 6 + 517 - 5 + 4 - 4 + 1)^4$
$:= (44 + 84 - 03 - 3 + 4 - 3 + 7 + 5)^5$	$:= (-45 - 1 - 6 + 517 - 5 - 4 + 4 + 1)^4$
$:= (4 - 4 + 84 + 03 + 3 + 43 + 7 - 5)^5$	$:= (45 - 1 - 6 - 5 - 1 - 7 - 5 + 441)^4$
$:= (-4 + 4 + 84 + 03 + 3 + 43 + 7 - 5)^5$	$:= (-4 + 516 + 5 + 1 - 7 - 5 - 44 - 1)^4$
$:= (4 + 4 + 8 + 4 + 033 + 4 + 3 + 75)^5$	$:= (-4 + 516 - 5 + 1 - 7 + 5 - 44 - 1)^4$
$:= (4 + 4 + 8 + 4 + 03 + 34 + 3 + 75)^5$	$:= (-4 + 516 + 5 - 1 - 7 - 5 - 44 + 1)^4$
$:= (44 + 8 + 4 + 033 + 4 + 37 + 5)^5$	$:= (4 + 516 - 5 + 1 - 7 - 5 - 44 + 1)^4$
$:= (44 + 8 + 4 + 03 + 34 + 37 + 5)^5$	$:= (-4 + 516 - 5 - 1 - 7 + 5 - 44 + 1)^4$
$:= (44 - 8 - 4 - 03 + 34 - 3 + 75)^5$	$:= (-4 + 516 + 5 + 1 - 7 - 5 - 4 - 41)^4$
$:= (-4 + 48 + 40 + 3 + 3 + 43 + 7 - 5)^5$	$:= (-4 + 516 - 5 + 1 - 7 + 5 - 4 - 41)^4$
$:= (4 + 48 + 4 + 033 + 4 + 37 + 5)^5$	$:= (-4 + 5 - 1 - 6 + 517 - 5 - 44 - 1)^4$
$:= (4 + 48 + 4 + 03 + 34 + 37 + 5)^5$	$:= (4 - 5 + 1 - 6 + 517 - 5 - 44 - 1)^4$
$:= (4 + 4 + 84 - 033 + 4 - 3 + 75)^5$	$:= (-4 - 5 - 1 - 6 + 517 + 5 - 44 - 1)^4$
$:= (4 + 4 + 8 + 40 + 33 + 4 + 37 + 5)^5$	$:= (4 - 5 - 1 - 6 + 517 - 5 - 44 + 1)^4$
$:= (4 + 4 + 8 + 40 + 3 + 34 + 37 + 5)^5$	$:= (-4 + 5 - 1 - 6 + 517 - 5 - 4 - 41)^4$
$:= (4 - 4 - 8 + 40 - 3 + 34 - 3 + 75)^5$	$:= (4 - 5 + 1 - 6 + 517 - 5 - 4 - 41)^4$
$:= (-4 + 4 - 8 + 40 - 3 + 34 - 3 + 75)^5$	$:= (-4 - 5 - 1 - 6 + 517 + 5 - 4 - 41)^4$
$:= (44 + 8 + 40 - 33 + 4 - 3 + 75)^5$	$:= (-4 - 5 + 1 - 6 + 517 - 5 + 4 - 41)^4$
$:= (4 + 48 + 40 - 33 + 4 - 3 + 75)^5$	$:= (451 - 65 + 1 + 75 + 4 - 4 - 1)^4$
$:= (4 + 4 - 8 + 403 - 343 + 75)^5$	$:= (451 - 65 + 1 + 75 - 4 + 4 - 1)^4$
$:= (-4 - 4 + 8 + 403 - 343 + 75)^5$	$:= (451 - 65 - 1 + 75 + 4 - 4 + 1)^4$
44852393377 $:= (4485 - 2 + 3 - 933 + 7 - 7)^3$	$:= (451 - 65 - 1 + 75 - 4 + 4 + 1)^4$
44852393377 $:= (4485 - 2 + 3 - 933 - 7 + 7)^3$	$:= (451 + 65 + 1 - 7 - 54 + 4 + 1)^4$
45004049693 $:= (-4 - 500 + 4049 + 6 + 9 - 3)^3$	$:= (451 + 6 + 51 - 7 + 5 - 44 - 1)^4$
45165175441 $:= (4 + 5 - 1 + 6 + 5 - 1 + 7 - 5 + 441)^4$	$:= (451 + 6 - 51 + 7 + 5 + 44 - 1)^4$
$:= (4 + 5 + 1 + 6 + 5 + 1 - 7 + 5 + 441)^4$	$:= (451 + 6 + 51 - 7 + 5 - 4 - 41)^4$
$:= (4 + 5 - 1 + 6 - 5 - 1 + 7 + 5 + 441)^4$	$:= (451 - 6 + 51 + 7 - 5 + 4 - 41)^4$
$:= (4 + 5 + 1 - 6 + 5 - 1 + 7 + 5 + 441)^4$	$:= (451 - 6 - 5 - 17 - 5 + 44 - 1)^4$
$:= (4 - 5 - 1 + 6 + 5 - 1 + 7 + 5 + 441)^4$	$:= (451 - 6 - 5 + 1 + 7 + 54 - 41)^4$
$:= (4 + 5 - 1 - 6 + 5 + 1 + 7 + 5 + 441)^4$	$:= (-45 - 1 + 65 - 1 + 7 - 5 + 441)^4$
$:= (451 - 6 + 5 + 17 - 5 + 4 - 4 - 1)^4$	$:= (-45 + 1 + 65 + 1 - 7 + 5 + 441)^4$
$:= (451 - 6 - 5 + 17 + 5 + 4 - 4 - 1)^4$	$:= (-45 + 1 + 6 - 51 + 7 + 544 - 1)^4$
$:= (451 - 6 + 5 + 17 - 5 - 4 + 4 - 1)^4$	$:= (-45 - 1 + 6 - 51 + 7 + 544 + 1)^4$
$:= (451 - 6 - 5 + 17 + 5 - 4 + 4 - 1)^4$	$:= (-4 - 51 + 6 - 5 - 1 + 75 + 441)^4$
$:= (451 - 6 - 5 + 17 - 5 + 4 + 4 + 1)^4$	$:= (-4 - 51 - 6 + 5 + 1 + 75 + 441)^4$
$:= (-45 - 1 - 6 + 517 + 5 - 4 - 4 - 1)^4$	$:= (4 + 5 - 16 + 517 - 54 + 4 + 1)^4$

$$\begin{aligned}
 &:= (4 + 5 - 16 + 5 + 17 + 5 + 441)^4 \\
 &:= (-4 + 5 - 1 - 65 - 17 + 544 - 1)^4 \\
 &:= (4 - 5 + 1 - 65 - 17 + 544 - 1)^4 \\
 &:= (4 - 5 - 1 - 65 - 17 + 544 + 1)^4 \\
 &:= (-4 + 5 + 1 - 6 - 51 + 75 + 441)^4 \\
 &:= (-4 - 5 - 1 + 6 - 51 + 75 + 441)^4 \\
 &:= (451 + 65 - 17 + 5 - 44 + 1)^4 \\
 &:= (-45 + 16 + 51 - 7 + 5 + 441)^4 \\
 &:= (-45 - 16 + 5 + 1 + 75 + 441)^4 \\
 &:= (-4 + 516 + 51 - 7 - 54 - 41)^4 \\
 \mathbf{45308387125} &:= (4 + 5 - 308 + 3871 - 2 - 5)^3 \\
 &:= (4 - 5 - 308 + 3871 - 2 + 5)^3 \\
 \mathbf{45422866432} &:= (4 + 5 + 4228 - 664 - 3 - 2)^3 \\
 &:= (4 - 5 + 4228 - 664 + 3 + 2)^3 \\
 &:= (-4 - 5 + 4228 - 6 - 643 - 2)^3 \\
 \mathbf{45558341136} &:= (455 + 5 + 8 - 3 + 4 + 1 + 1 - 3 - 6)^4 \\
 &:= (455 + 5 + 8 + 3 - 4 - 1 - 1 + 3 - 6)^4 \\
 &:= (455 - 5 + 8 + 3 + 4 + 1 - 1 + 3 - 6)^4 \\
 &:= (455 - 5 + 8 + 3 + 4 - 1 + 1 + 3 - 6)^4 \\
 &:= (455 + 5 + 8 - 3 - 4 - 1 - 1 - 3 + 6)^4 \\
 &:= (455 - 5 + 8 - 3 + 4 + 1 - 1 - 3 + 6)^4 \\
 &:= (455 + 5 - 8 + 3 + 4 + 1 - 1 - 3 + 6)^4 \\
 &:= (455 - 5 + 8 - 3 + 4 - 1 + 1 - 3 + 6)^4 \\
 &:= (455 + 5 - 8 + 3 + 4 - 1 + 1 - 3 + 6)^4 \\
 &:= (455 - 5 + 8 + 3 - 4 + 1 + 1 - 3 + 6)^4 \\
 &:= (455 + 5 - 8 - 3 + 4 + 1 - 1 + 3 + 6)^4 \\
 &:= (455 + 5 - 8 - 3 + 4 - 1 + 1 + 3 + 6)^4 \\
 &:= (455 - 5 + 8 - 3 - 4 + 1 + 1 + 3 + 6)^4 \\
 &:= (455 + 5 - 8 + 3 - 4 + 1 + 1 + 3 + 6)^4 \\
 &:= (45 + 5 + 5 + 8 - 3 + 411 - 3 - 6)^4 \\
 &:= (455 - 5 - 8 + 34 - 11 + 3 - 6)^4 \\
 &:= (455 - 5 + 8 - 34 + 1 + 1 + 36)^4 \\
 &:= (-45 + 5 + 5 + 83 + 411 - 3 + 6)^4 \\
 &:= (-4 + 555 - 83 - 4 - 11 + 3 + 6)^4 \\
 &:= (4 + 555 - 83 + 4 + 1 - 13 - 6)^4 \\
 &:= (-4 + 555 - 8 - 3 - 41 - 1 - 36)^4 \\
 &:= (4 + 55 + 58 + 341 + 1 - 3 + 6)^4 \\
 &:= (4 - 5 - 5 + 583 + 4 - 113 - 6)^4
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 &:= (455 + 58 - 3 - 41 - 13 + 6)^4 \\
 &:= (-45 + 558 - 3 - 41 - 13 + 6)^4 \\
 &:= (-45 + 55 + 8 - 3 + 411 + 36)^4 \\
 &:= (-45 + 5 + 58 - 3 + 411 + 36)^4 \\
 &:= (-4 + 555 - 83 - 41 - 1 + 36)^4 \\
 &:= (-4 + 555 - 8 - 34 - 11 - 36)^4 \\
 &:= (455 - 5 - 83 - 41 + 136)^4 \\
 &:= (45 + 558 - 34 - 113 + 6)^4 \\
 \mathbf{45614093517} &:= (4 + 56 + 1 + 4 - 09 + 3517)^3 \\
 &:= (-4 + 56 - 1 - 4 + 09 + 3517)^3 \\
 &:= (45 + 6 + 14 - 09 + 3517)^3 \\
 \mathbf{45652403224} &:= (45 + 65 + 240 + 3224)^3 \\
 \mathbf{45690734375} &:= (4 + 56 + 90 - 7 + 3437 - 5)^3 \\
 \mathbf{45844273539} &:= (45 + 8 - 4 - 4 + 2 - 7 + 3539)^3 \\
 &:= (45 - 8 + 4 + 4 + 2 - 7 + 3539)^3 \\
 &:= (4 + 5 - 8 + 44 + 2 - 7 + 3539)^3 \\
 &:= (4 - 5 - 8 + 44 - 2 + 7 + 3539)^3 \\
 &:= (-4 + 5 + 8 - 4 + 42 - 7 + 3539)^3 \\
 &:= (4 + 5 - 8 + 4 + 42 - 7 + 3539)^3 \\
 &:= (-45 + 84 - 4 - 2 + 7 + 3539)^3 \\
 &:= (-4 - 5 + 84 - 42 + 7 + 3539)^3 \\
 \mathbf{45954068161} &:= (459 - 5 - 4 + 06 - 8 + 16 - 1)^4 \\
 &:= (459 + 5 - 4 - 06 - 8 + 16 + 1)^4 \\
 &:= (45 + 9 + 5 + 406 - 8 + 1 + 6 - 1)^4 \\
 &:= (45 + 9 + 5 + 406 - 8 - 1 + 6 + 1)^4 \\
 &:= (45 - 9 + 5 + 406 + 8 + 1 + 6 + 1)^4 \\
 &:= (4 - 59 + 540 - 6 - 8 - 1 - 6 - 1)^4 \\
 &:= (-4 + 5 + 9 - 5 + 406 - 8 - 1 + 61)^4 \\
 &:= (4 + 5 - 9 + 5 + 406 - 8 - 1 + 61)^4 \\
 &:= (-4 - 5 + 9 + 5 + 406 - 8 - 1 + 61)^4 \\
 &:= (4 - 5 + 9 - 5 + 406 - 8 + 1 + 61)^4 \\
 &:= (-4 + 5 - 9 - 5 + 406 + 8 + 1 + 61)^4 \\
 &:= (-4 - 5 - 9 + 5 + 406 + 8 + 1 + 61)^4 \\
 &:= (459 - 54 + 06 - 8 - 1 + 61)^4 \\
 &:= (459 - 5 + 40 - 6 - 8 - 16 - 1)^4 \\
 &:= (-45 + 9 + 5 + 406 + 81 + 6 + 1)^4 \\
 &:= (-4 + 59 - 5 + 406 - 8 + 16 - 1)^4 \\
 &:= (4 - 5 + 9 + 540 - 68 - 16 - 1)^4
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} &:= (-45 + 95 + 406 - 8 + 16 - 1)^4 \\ &:= (-4 - 59 + 540 + 6 - 81 + 61)^4 \\ &:= (4 - 5 - 95 + 406 - 8 + 161)^4 \\ \mathbf{45959653368} &:= (45 + 95 + 9 + 65 + 3368)^3 \\ \mathbf{45998156287} &:= (-4 + 59 + 9815 - 6287)^3 \\ \mathbf{46036680704} &:= (-4 - 6 + 03668 - 070 - 4)^3 \\ \mathbf{46190993472} &:= (4 - 6 + 19 + 099 + 3472)^3 \\ \mathbf{46306954071} &:= (-4 - 6 + 3069 + 540 - 7 - 1)^3 \\ \mathbf{46345650688} &:= (4 + 6 + 3456 + 50 + 68 + 8)^3 \\ \mathbf{46352367616} &:= (463 + 5 + 2 + 3 + 6 + 7 - 6 - 16)^4 \\ &:= (463 + 5 + 2 + 3 - 6 + 7 + 6 - 16)^4 \\ &:= (463 + 5 + 2 - 3 - 6 - 7 - 6 + 16)^4 \\ &:= (463 - 5 - 2 - 3 - 6 + 7 - 6 + 16)^4 \\ &:= (-46 - 3 + 523 - 6 + 7 - 6 + 1 - 6)^4 \\ &:= (4 - 63 + 523 + 6 + 7 - 6 - 1 - 6)^4 \\ &:= (4 - 63 + 523 - 6 + 7 + 6 - 1 - 6)^4 \\ &:= (4 - 63 + 523 + 6 - 7 + 6 + 1 - 6)^4 \\ &:= (4 - 63 + 523 - 6 + 7 - 6 - 1 + 6)^4 \\ &:= (4 - 63 + 523 + 6 - 7 - 6 + 1 + 6)^4 \\ &:= (4 - 63 + 523 - 6 - 7 + 6 + 1 + 6)^4 \\ &:= (4 + 6 - 3 + 523 - 67 + 6 + 1 - 6)^4 \\ &:= (4 + 6 - 3 + 523 - 67 - 6 + 1 + 6)^4 \\ &:= (4 - 6 - 3 + 523 - 67 + 6 + 1 + 6)^4 \\ &:= (4 + 6 - 3 + 523 - 6 + 7 - 61 - 6)^4 \\ &:= (4 - 6 - 3 + 523 + 6 + 7 - 61 - 6)^4 \\ &:= (4 - 6 - 3 + 523 - 6 + 7 - 61 + 6)^4 \\ &:= (463 - 52 - 3 + 67 - 6 + 1 - 6)^4 \\ &:= (463 + 52 + 3 - 67 + 6 + 1 + 6)^4 \\ &:= (463 + 52 + 3 + 6 + 7 - 61 - 6)^4 \\ &:= (463 - 52 - 3 - 6 + 7 + 61 - 6)^4 \\ &:= (463 + 52 + 3 - 6 + 7 - 61 + 6)^4 \\ &:= (46 + 352 + 3 - 6 + 76 - 1 - 6)^4 \\ &:= (46 + 3 - 5 - 2 + 367 + 61 - 6)^4 \\ &:= (-4 + 6 + 352 + 36 + 7 + 61 + 6)^4 \\ &:= (4 + 6 - 3 + 523 - 6 - 76 + 16)^4 \\ &:= (4 - 6 - 3 + 523 + 6 - 76 + 16)^4 \\ &:= (463 + 52 - 36 + 7 - 6 - 16)^4 \\ &:= (463 - 52 + 36 + 7 - 6 + 16)^4 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} &:= (463 + 52 + 3 + 6 - 76 + 16)^4 \\ &:= (46 - 352 - 3 + 6 + 761 + 6)^4 \\ &:= (-4 + 635 - 236 + 76 - 1 - 6)^4 \\ &:= (4 - 63 + 523 + 67 - 61 - 6)^4 \\ &:= (4 - 63 + 523 - 67 + 61 + 6)^4 \\ &:= (4 + 63 + 52 + 367 - 6 - 16)^4 \\ &:= (-4 - 63 + 5 - 23 - 67 + 616)^4 \\ \mathbf{46384368857} &:= (4 - 6 + 3 - 84 + 3688 - 5 - 7)^3 \\ &:= (-4 - 6 - 3 - 84 + 3688 - 5 + 7)^3 \\ \mathbf{46525874176} &:= (46 + 52 + 5 + 8 + 7 + 4 + 1 + 7 + 6)^5 \\ &:= (46 + 5 + 2 + 58 + 7 + 4 + 1 + 7 + 6)^5 \\ &:= (46 + 5 - 2 + 5 + 8 + 74 - 1 + 7 - 6)^5 \\ &:= (46 + 5 - 2 + 5 + 8 + 74 + 1 - 7 + 6)^5 \\ &:= (46 + 5 + 2 + 5 - 8 + 74 - 1 + 7 + 6)^5 \\ &:= (46 + 5 + 2 + 5 - 8 + 7 + 4 - 1 + 76)^5 \\ &:= (46 + 5 + 2 - 5 + 8 + 7 - 4 + 1 + 76)^5 \\ &:= (46 - 5 + 2 + 5 + 8 + 7 - 4 + 1 + 76)^5 \\ &:= (46 + 5 - 2 + 5 + 8 - 7 + 4 + 1 + 76)^5 \\ &:= (4 + 65 - 2 + 58 + 7 + 4 - 1 + 7 - 6)^5 \\ &:= (4 + 65 - 2 + 58 + 7 + 4 + 1 - 7 + 6)^5 \\ &:= (-4 + 65 + 2 + 58 + 7 - 4 - 1 + 7 + 6)^5 \\ &:= (4 + 65 - 2 + 58 - 7 + 4 + 1 + 7 + 6)^5 \\ &:= (-4 + 65 + 2 + 5 + 8 + 74 - 1 - 7 - 6)^5 \\ &:= (4 + 65 + 2 - 5 + 8 + 74 + 1 - 7 - 6)^5 \\ &:= (-4 + 65 - 2 - 5 + 8 + 74 - 1 + 7 - 6)^5 \\ &:= (-4 + 65 + 2 + 5 - 8 + 74 + 1 + 7 - 6)^5 \\ &:= (4 + 65 - 2 + 5 - 8 + 74 - 1 - 7 + 6)^5 \\ &:= (-4 + 65 - 2 - 5 + 8 + 74 + 1 - 7 + 6)^5 \\ &:= (-4 + 65 + 2 - 5 - 8 + 74 - 1 + 7 + 6)^5 \\ &:= (-4 + 65 - 2 + 5 + 8 - 7 - 4 - 1 + 76)^5 \\ &:= (4 + 65 + 2 - 5 - 8 + 7 - 4 - 1 + 76)^5 \\ &:= (4 + 65 - 2 + 5 - 8 - 7 + 4 - 1 + 76)^5 \\ &:= (-4 + 65 + 2 - 5 - 8 + 7 + 4 - 1 + 76)^5 \\ &:= (4 + 65 - 2 - 5 + 8 - 7 - 4 + 1 + 76)^5 \\ &:= (-4 + 65 - 2 + 5 - 8 + 7 - 4 + 1 + 76)^5 \\ &:= (-4 + 65 - 2 - 5 + 8 - 7 + 4 + 1 + 76)^5 \\ &:= (4 + 6 + 52 + 5 + 87 - 4 - 1 - 7 - 6)^5 \\ &:= (-4 + 6 + 52 + 5 + 87 + 4 - 1 - 7 - 6)^5 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} &:= (4 + 6 + 52 - 5 + 87 + 4 + 1 - 7 - 6)^5 \\ &:= (4 - 6 + 52 - 5 + 87 + 4 - 1 + 7 - 6)^5 \\ &:= (4 - 6 + 52 + 5 + 87 - 4 - 1 - 7 + 6)^5 \\ &:= (-4 - 6 + 52 + 5 + 87 + 4 - 1 - 7 + 6)^5 \\ &:= (4 - 6 + 52 - 5 + 87 + 4 + 1 - 7 + 6)^5 \\ &:= (4 + 6 + 52 + 5 + 8 + 7 + 41 + 7 + 6)^5 \\ &:= (4 + 6 + 5 + 25 + 8 + 74 + 1 + 7 + 6)^5 \\ &:= (4 + 6 + 5 + 25 + 8 + 7 + 4 + 1 + 76)^5 \\ &:= (4 + 6 + 5 + 2 + 58 + 7 + 41 + 7 + 6)^5 \\ &:= (4 + 6 + 5 + 2 + 5 + 87 + 4 + 17 + 6)^5 \\ &:= (-4 - 6 - 5 - 2 - 5 + 87 - 4 - 1 + 76)^5 \\ &:= (4 + 6 + 5 - 2 + 5 + 8 - 7 + 41 + 76)^5 \\ &:= (-4 + 6 + 5 + 2 - 5 + 8 + 7 + 41 + 76)^5 \\ &:= (-4 + 6 - 5 + 2 + 5 + 8 + 7 + 41 + 76)^5 \\ &:= (46 + 52 - 5 + 8 + 7 + 41 - 7 - 6)^5 \\ &:= (46 + 52 - 5 + 8 - 7 + 41 + 7 - 6)^5 \\ &:= (46 - 5 + 25 + 8 + 74 + 1 - 7 - 6)^5 \\ &:= (46 - 5 + 25 - 8 + 7 - 4 - 1 + 76)^5 \\ &:= (46 - 5 + 2 + 58 + 7 + 41 - 7 - 6)^5 \\ &:= (46 - 5 + 2 + 58 - 7 + 41 + 7 - 6)^5 \\ &:= (46 - 5 - 2 - 5 + 87 + 4 + 17 - 6)^5 \\ &:= (46 - 5 - 2 - 5 - 8 - 7 + 41 + 76)^5 \\ &:= (4 + 65 + 25 + 8 + 7 + 4 + 17 + 6)^5 \\ &:= (4 + 65 + 2 + 5 + 87 - 4 - 17 - 6)^5 \\ &:= (-4 + 65 + 2 + 5 + 87 + 4 - 17 - 6)^5 \\ &:= (-4 + 65 - 2 + 5 + 87 - 4 - 17 + 6)^5 \\ &:= (-4 - 6 + 52 + 5 - 8 + 74 + 17 - 6)^5 \\ &:= (4 + 6 - 52 + 5 + 8 - 7 - 4 + 176)^5 \\ &:= (-4 + 6 - 52 + 5 + 8 - 7 + 4 + 176)^5 \\ &:= (4 - 6 - 52 - 5 + 8 + 7 + 4 + 176)^5 \\ &:= (4 + 6 - 5 + 25 + 87 - 4 + 17 + 6)^5 \\ &:= (-4 + 6 - 5 + 25 + 87 + 4 + 17 + 6)^5 \\ &:= (4 - 6 + 5 - 25 + 87 - 4 - 1 + 76)^5 \\ &:= (-4 - 6 + 5 - 25 + 87 + 4 - 1 + 76)^5 \\ &:= (4 - 6 - 5 - 25 + 87 + 4 + 1 + 76)^5 \\ &:= (4 - 6 - 5 + 25 + 8 - 7 + 41 + 76)^5 \\ &:= (-4 - 6 + 5 + 25 - 8 + 7 + 41 + 76)^5 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} &:= (-4 - 6 + 5 - 2 + 58 + 74 + 17 - 6)^5 \\ &:= (4 + 6 - 5 + 2 - 58 + 7 + 4 + 176)^5 \\ &:= (-4 + 6 + 5 + 2 + 5 + 87 - 41 + 76)^5 \\ &:= (-465 - 2 + 587 + 4 - 1 + 7 + 6)^5 \\ &:= (-46 + 52 + 58 + 74 - 1 - 7 + 6)^5 \\ &:= (46 + 52 + 58 + 7 - 4 - 17 - 6)^5 \\ &:= (-46 + 52 + 58 - 7 + 4 - 1 + 76)^5 \\ &:= (46 + 52 + 5 + 87 - 41 - 7 - 6)^5 \\ &:= (46 + 52 - 5 - 8 + 74 - 17 - 6)^5 \\ &:= (46 + 5 + 25 + 87 - 4 - 17 - 6)^5 \\ &:= (46 - 5 + 2 - 58 + 74 + 1 + 76)^5 \\ &:= (4 - 65 + 258 - 7 - 41 - 7 - 6)^5 \\ &:= (-4 + 65 + 25 + 8 + 7 - 41 + 76)^5 \\ &:= (-4 - 65 - 2 + 58 + 74 - 1 + 76)^5 \\ &:= (4 - 65 - 2 - 5 + 87 + 41 + 76)^5 \\ &:= (4 - 6 + 52 + 58 - 7 - 41 + 76)^5 \\ &:= (465 + 2 + 5 + 87 - 417 - 6)^5 \\ &:= (46 + 5 + 258 + 7 - 4 - 176)^5 \\ &:= (46 + 5 - 25 + 8 - 74 + 176)^5 \\ &:= (-4 - 652 - 5 + 874 - 1 - 76)^5 \\ &46582157241 := (46 + 58 + 215724 + 1)^2 \\ &46656000000 := (4 + 6 - 6 + 56 + 000000)^6 \\ &:= (4 - 6 + 6 + 56 + 000000)^6 \\ &46733803208 := (4 + 6 + 7 + 3380 - 3 + 208)^3 \\ &:= (4 + 6 + 7 - 3 + 380 + 3208)^3 \\ &46753250625 := (467 + 5 + 3 - 2 + 5 - 06 - 2 - 5)^4 \\ &:= (467 + 5 - 3 + 2 - 5 + 06 - 2 - 5)^4 \\ &:= (467 - 5 - 3 + 2 + 5 + 06 - 2 - 5)^4 \\ &:= (467 + 5 - 3 - 2 - 5 + 06 + 2 - 5)^4 \\ &:= (467 - 5 + 3 + 2 - 5 + 06 + 2 - 5)^4 \\ &:= (467 - 5 - 3 - 2 + 5 + 06 + 2 - 5)^4 \\ &:= (467 + 5 + 3 - 2 - 5 - 06 - 2 + 5)^4 \\ &:= (467 - 5 + 3 - 2 + 5 - 06 - 2 + 5)^4 \\ &:= (467 - 5 - 3 + 2 - 5 + 06 - 2 + 5)^4 \\ &:= (467 - 5 - 3 - 2 - 5 + 06 + 2 + 5)^4 \\ &:= (-46 - 7 + 532 - 5 - 06 + 2 - 5)^4 \\ &:= (-4 - 67 + 532 + 5 + 06 - 2 - 5)^4 \\ &:= (4 - 67 + 532 + 5 - 06 + 2 - 5)^4 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} &:= (-4 - 67 + 532 - 5 + 06 - 2 + 5)^4 \\ &:= (4 - 67 + 532 - 5 - 06 + 2 + 5)^4 \\ &:= (4 - 6 + 7 + 532 - 5 - 062 - 5)^4 \\ &:= (-4 + 6 - 7 + 532 + 5 - 062 - 5)^4 \\ &:= (-4 + 6 - 7 + 532 - 5 - 062 + 5)^4 \\ &:= (4 + 6 + 7 - 53 + 2 + 506 - 2 - 5)^4 \\ &:= (4 + 6 + 7 - 53 - 2 + 506 + 2 - 5)^4 \\ &:= (4 + 6 - 7 - 53 + 2 + 506 + 2 + 5)^4 \\ &:= (4 + 6 - 7 - 5 - 32 + 506 - 2 - 5)^4 \\ &:= (-4 - 6 - 7 + 5 - 32 + 506 - 2 + 5)^4 \\ &:= (467 - 53 + 2 + 50 + 6 - 2 - 5)^4 \\ &:= (467 - 53 - 2 + 50 + 6 + 2 - 5)^4 \\ &:= (467 + 53 - 2 - 50 - 6 - 2 + 5)^4 \\ &:= (467 - 5 - 3 + 25 + 06 - 25)^4 \\ &:= (467 - 5 - 3 - 25 + 06 + 25)^4 \\ &:= (46 - 75 - 3 - 2 + 506 - 2 - 5)^4 \\ &:= (-46 - 7 + 532 + 5 + 06 - 25)^4 \\ &:= (-4 - 67 + 5 + 32 + 506 - 2 - 5)^4 \\ &:= (-4 - 67 - 5 + 32 + 506 - 2 + 5)^4 \\ &:= (4 - 6 + 75 + 325 + 062 + 5)^4 \\ &:= (4 + 6 - 75 - 3 + 2 + 506 + 25)^4 \\ &:= (46 + 75 + 325 - 06 + 25)^4 \\ &:= (46 - 7 - 53 - 2 + 506 - 25)^4 \\ &:= (-46 - 7 + 5 + 32 + 506 - 25)^4 \\ &:= (-46 + 7 + 5 - 32 + 506 + 25)^4 \\ &:= (-4 - 67 + 53 + 2 + 506 - 25)^4 \\ \mathbf{46811692864} &:= (4 - 6 + 811 - 69 + 2864)^3 \\ \mathbf{46892170116} &:= (-468 + 9 + 217011 - 6)^2 \\ \mathbf{47156728336} &:= (471 + 5 + 6 + 7 + 2 + 8 + 3 - 36)^4 \\ &:= (471 + 5 - 6 + 7 + 28 - 33 - 6)^4 \\ &:= (471 - 5 - 6 + 7 - 28 + 33 - 6)^4 \\ &:= (471 - 5 + 6 - 7 + 28 - 33 + 6)^4 \\ &:= (471 + 5 - 6 + 7 + 28 - 3 - 36)^4 \\ &:= (47 + 1 + 5 + 67 + 2 + 8 + 336)^4 \\ &:= (4 - 71 + 567 - 28 + 3 - 3 - 6)^4 \\ &:= (4 - 71 + 567 - 28 - 3 + 3 - 6)^4 \\ &:= (4 + 71 + 56 - 7 - 2 + 8 + 336)^4 \\ &:= (-4 + 71 + 5 - 6 + 72 - 8 + 336)^4 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} &:= (4 + 7 + 156 + 7 + 283 + 3 + 6)^4 \\ &:= (4 + 7 - 1 + 56 + 72 - 8 + 336)^4 \\ &:= (471 - 5 + 67 - 28 - 33 - 6)^4 \\ &:= (471 - 5 - 67 + 28 + 33 + 6)^4 \\ &:= (471 - 5 + 67 - 28 - 3 - 36)^4 \\ &:= (471 - 5 - 67 + 28 + 3 + 36)^4 \\ &:= (-47 + 1 + 567 - 28 - 33 + 6)^4 \\ &:= (4 + 71 + 5 + 67 + 283 + 36)^4 \\ &:= (4 + 71 + 5 - 6 + 728 - 336)^4 \\ &:= (-47 + 156 - 7 + 28 + 336)^4 \\ \mathbf{47359345032} &:= (4 + 7 + 3593 + 4 + 5 + 03 + 2)^3 \\ &:= (4 + 7 + 3593 - 4 + 50 - 32)^3 \\ &:= (-4 + 7 + 3593 + 4 + 50 - 32)^3 \\ &:= (47 + 3593 - 4 - 50 + 32)^3 \\ &:= (4 + 73 + 59 + 3450 + 32)^3 \\ \mathbf{47398625659} &:= (4 + 73 + 986 + 2565 - 9)^3 \\ \mathbf{47437928000} &:= (4 - 7 - 4379 + 2 + 8000)^3 \\ \mathbf{47562811921} &:= (475 - 6 + 2 + 8 + 1 - 1 - 9 - 2 - 1)^4 \\ &:= (475 - 6 + 2 + 8 - 1 + 1 - 9 - 2 - 1)^4 \\ &:= (475 - 6 + 2 - 8 - 1 - 1 + 9 - 2 - 1)^4 \\ &:= (475 - 6 - 2 - 8 + 1 + 1 + 9 - 2 - 1)^4 \\ &:= (475 + 6 + 2 - 8 + 1 - 1 - 9 + 2 - 1)^4 \\ &:= (475 - 6 - 2 + 8 + 1 - 1 - 9 + 2 - 1)^4 \\ &:= (475 + 6 + 2 - 8 - 1 + 1 - 9 + 2 - 1)^4 \\ &:= (475 - 6 - 2 + 8 - 1 + 1 - 9 + 2 - 1)^4 \\ &:= (475 - 6 - 2 - 8 - 1 - 1 + 9 + 2 - 1)^4 \\ &:= (475 - 6 + 2 + 8 - 1 - 1 - 9 - 2 + 1)^4 \\ &:= (475 + 6 + 2 - 8 + 1 + 1 - 9 - 2 + 1)^4 \\ &:= (475 - 6 - 2 + 8 + 1 + 1 - 9 - 2 + 1)^4 \\ &:= (475 - 6 - 2 - 8 + 1 - 1 + 9 - 2 + 1)^4 \\ &:= (475 + 6 + 2 - 8 - 1 - 1 - 9 + 2 + 1)^4 \\ &:= (475 - 6 - 2 + 8 - 1 - 1 - 9 + 2 + 1)^4 \\ &:= (475 + 6 - 2 - 8 + 1 + 1 - 9 + 2 + 1)^4 \\ &:= (475 - 6 + 2 + 8 + 1 - 1 + 9 - 21)^4 \\ &:= (475 - 6 + 2 + 8 - 1 + 1 + 9 - 21)^4 \\ &:= (4 - 7 + 562 - 81 + 1 - 9 - 2 - 1)^4 \end{aligned}$$

$:= (4 - 7 + 562 - 81 - 1 - 9 - 2 + 1)^4$	$:= (479 - 7 - 15 + 1 + 2 - 5 + 7 + 6)^4$
$:= (475 + 62 - 81 + 1 + 9 + 2 - 1)^4$	$:= (479 - 7 - 1 + 5 - 12 + 5 - 7 + 6)^4$
$:= (475 + 62 - 81 - 1 + 9 + 2 + 1)^4$	$:= (-47 - 9 + 7 - 1 + 512 + 5 + 7 - 6)^4$
$:= (475 - 6 + 28 + 1 - 1 - 9 - 21)^4$	$:= (-47 - 9 + 7 + 1 + 512 + 5 - 7 + 6)^4$
$:= (475 - 6 + 28 - 1 + 1 - 9 - 21)^4$	$:= (-47 - 9 - 7 + 1 + 512 + 5 + 7 + 6)^4$
$:= (475 + 6 - 28 + 1 + 1 - 9 + 21)^4$	$:= (479 - 7 - 15 - 1 + 25 - 7 - 6)^4$
$:= (4 - 7 + 562 - 81 + 1 + 9 - 21)^4$	$:= (-4 - 79 - 7 - 15 - 1 - 2 + 576)^4$
$:= (475 + 62 - 81 - 1 - 9 + 21)^4$	$:= (-4 - 79 - 7 - 1 - 5 - 12 + 576)^4$
$:= (-4 - 75 + 628 + 11 - 92 - 1)^4$	$:= (-4 + 7 + 971 - 512 + 5 + 7 - 6)^4$
$:= (4 + 7 + 562 - 8 - 119 + 21)^4$	$:= (-4 + 7 - 97 - 15 - 1 + 2 + 576)^4$
$:= (4 - 756 + 28 + 1192 - 1)^4$	$:= (-4 + 7 - 97 - 1 + 512 + 57 - 6)^4$
47595354624 $:= (-47 + 5 - 953 - 5 + 4624)^3$	$:= (-4 - 7 - 97 + 1 + 512 + 57 + 6)^4$
$:= (-47 - 5 - 953 + 5 + 4624)^3$	$:= (4 - 7 - 97 - 1 + 5 - 12 + 576)^4$
47713652883 $:= (-4 - 7 + 71 + 3652 - 88 + 3)^3$	$:= (-4 + 7 + 9 - 71 - 51 + 2 + 576)^4$
$:= (4 + 771 - 36 + 5 + 2883)^3$	$:= (-4 - 7 - 9 - 71 - 5 - 12 + 576)^4$
47753129152 $:= (477 + 5 + 3129 + 15 + 2)^3$	$:= (47 - 9 + 7 - 151 - 2 + 576)^4$
47971512576 $:= (-4 - 7 - 9 - 7 + 1 + 512 - 5 - 7 - 6)^4$	$:= (-4 - 797 + 1 + 5 + 1257 + 6)^4$
$:= (479 - 7 + 15 + 1 - 2 - 5 - 7 - 6)^4$	$:= (4 + 79 + 71 + 51 + 257 + 6)^4$
$:= (479 + 7 - 15 - 1 + 2 - 5 + 7 - 6)^4$	
$:= (479 + 7 - 15 + 1 + 2 - 5 - 7 + 6)^4$	
47990444104 $:= (-479 + 9 + 04 - 4 + 4104)^3$	$:= (4 + 82 - 6 + 1 - 7 - 2 + 4 + 4 + 57)^5$
$:= (-479 + 9 - 04 + 4 + 4104)^3$	$:= (4 + 8 + 2 + 61 + 72 - 4 - 4 + 5 - 7)^5$
$:= (-4 - 799 + 04441 - 04)^3$	$:= (-4 + 8 + 2 + 61 + 72 + 4 - 4 + 5 - 7)^5$
48069723456 $:= (4806 + 9 - 723 - 456)^3$	$:= (-4 + 8 + 2 + 61 + 72 - 4 + 4 + 5 - 7)^5$
48261724457 $:= (48 + 2 + 6 - 1 + 72 + 4 + 4 - 5 + 7)^5$	$:= (4 - 8 + 2 + 61 + 72 + 4 + 4 + 5 - 7)^5$
$:= (48 - 2 + 6 + 1 + 72 + 4 - 4 + 5 + 7)^5$	$:= (4 + 8 - 2 + 61 + 72 - 4 - 4 - 5 + 7)^5$
$:= (48 - 2 + 6 + 1 + 72 - 4 + 4 + 5 + 7)^5$	$:= (-4 + 8 - 2 + 61 + 72 + 4 - 4 - 5 + 7)^5$
$:= (48 + 2 - 6 + 1 + 72 + 4 + 4 + 5 + 7)^5$	$:= (-4 + 8 - 2 + 61 + 72 - 4 + 4 - 5 + 7)^5$
$:= (-4 + 82 + 6 + 1 + 72 - 4 - 4 - 5 - 7)^5$	$:= (4 - 8 - 2 + 61 + 72 + 4 + 4 - 5 + 7)^5$
$:= (-4 + 82 - 6 - 1 + 72 - 4 - 4 - 5 + 7)^5$	$:= (4 + 8 + 2 + 61 + 7 - 2 + 4 - 4 + 57)^5$
$:= (-4 + 82 + 6 - 1 + 7 - 2 - 4 - 4 + 57)^5$	$:= (4 + 8 - 2 + 61 + 7 + 2 + 4 - 4 + 57)^5$
$:= (4 + 82 + 6 + 1 - 7 + 2 - 4 - 4 + 57)^5$	$:= (4 + 8 + 2 + 61 + 7 - 2 - 4 + 4 + 57)^5$
$:= (4 + 82 - 6 - 1 + 7 + 2 - 4 - 4 + 57)^5$	$:= (4 + 8 - 2 + 61 + 7 + 2 - 4 + 4 + 57)^5$
$:= (-4 + 82 + 6 + 1 - 7 + 2 + 4 - 4 + 57)^5$	$:= (-4 + 8 + 2 + 61 + 7 - 2 + 4 + 4 + 57)^5$
$:= (-4 + 82 - 6 - 1 + 7 + 2 + 4 - 4 + 57)^5$	$:= (-4 + 8 - 2 + 61 + 7 + 2 + 4 + 4 + 57)^5$
$:= (-4 + 82 + 6 + 1 - 7 + 2 - 4 + 4 + 57)^5$	$:= (4 + 8 + 2 + 6 - 1 + 72 + 44 - 5 + 7)^5$
$:= (-4 + 82 - 6 - 1 + 7 + 2 - 4 + 4 + 57)^5$	$:= (4 + 8 + 2 - 6 + 1 + 72 + 44 + 5 + 7)^5$

$$\begin{aligned}
 &:= (-4+8-2+6+1+72+44+5+7)^5 \\
 &:= (4+8-2+6+1+72-4+45+7)^5 \\
 &:= (4+8+2-6+1+72+4+45+7)^5 \\
 &:= (-4+8-2+6+1+72+4+45+7)^5 \\
 &:= (48+26+1+72-4-4+5-7)^5 \\
 &:= (48+26+1+7-2+4-4+57)^5 \\
 &:= (48+26+1+7-2-4+4+57)^5 \\
 &:= (48-2+6+1+7+24-4+57)^5 \\
 &:= (48+2-6+1+7+24+4+57)^5 \\
 &:= (48+2-6+1-7-2+44+57)^5 \\
 &:= (48-2-6+1-7+2+44+57)^5 \\
 &:= (4+82-6+17+24+4+5+7)^5 \\
 &:= (4+82-6+17-2+44+5-7)^5 \\
 &:= (-4+82-6+17+2+44-5+7)^5 \\
 &:= (-4+82+6+17+2-4+45-7)^5 \\
 &:= (4+82-6+17-2+4+45-7)^5 \\
 &:= (4+82+6+1+7-24+4+57)^5 \\
 &:= (4-8+26+1+72+44+5-7)^5 \\
 &:= (-4+8+26+1+72-4+45-7)^5 \\
 &:= (4-8+26+1+72+4+45-7)^5 \\
 &:= (-4+8+26+1+7-2+44+57)^5 \\
 &:= (-4+8+2+61-7+24-4+57)^5 \\
 &:= (4-8+2+61-7+24+4+57)^5 \\
 &:= (-482+617-2-4-4+5+7)^5 \\
 &:= (-48+261-72+4+4-5-7)^5 \\
 &:= (48+26+17-2-4+45+7)^5 \\
 &:= (48-26+1+72+44+5-7)^5 \\
 &:= (48-26+1+72+4+45-7)^5 \\
 &:= (48+2+61+72-44+5-7)^5 \\
 &:= (48-2+61+72-44-5+7)^5 \\
 &:= (48-2+61+72-4-45+7)^5 \\
 &:= (48-2+61-7-24+4+57)^5 \\
 &:= (48+2-6+17+24+45+7)^5 \\
 &:= (-48-2+6+1-7+244-57)^5 \\
 &:= (-48-2-6-1+7+244-57)^5 \\
 &:= (-4+82-61+72-4+45+7)^5 \\
 &:= (4-82-6+172-4-4+57)^5 \\
 &:= (-4-82-6+172+4-4+57)^5
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 &:= (-4-82-6+172-4+4+57)^5 \\
 &:= (-4-82-6-17+244-5+7)^5 \\
 &:= (4+82+6-17+24+45-7)^5 \\
 &:= (4+82+6+17-24+45+7)^5 \\
 &:= (-4+8+261-72-44-5-7)^5 \\
 &:= (-4+8+261-72-4-45-7)^5 \\
 &:= (4-8+261-72+4-45-7)^5 \\
 &:= (-4+8+26+172-4-4-57)^5 \\
 &:= (4-8+26+172+4-4-57)^5 \\
 &:= (4-8+26+172-4+4-57)^5 \\
 &:= (-4-8+26+172+4+4-57)^5 \\
 &:= (48-26+172+4-4-57)^5 \\
 &:= (48-26+172-4+4-57)^5 \\
 &:= (-4+826+1-724+45-7)^5 \\
 &:= (-4+8-26+172+44-57)^5 \\
 &:= (-482-6+172-4+457)^5 \\
 &:= (-48+26+172+44-57)^5 \\
 &48382841521 := (483+8-2-8+4-15-2+1)^4 \\
 &:= (483-8-2+8+4-15-2+1)^4 \\
 &:= (483+8+2-8-4-15+2+1)^4 \\
 &:= (483-8+2+8-4-15+2+1)^4 \\
 &:= (48+3+8+2-8+415+2-1)^4 \\
 &:= (48+3-8+2+8+415+2-1)^4 \\
 &:= (-48+3+8-2-8-4-1+521)^4 \\
 &:= (-48+3-8-2+8-4-1+521)^4 \\
 &:= (-48-3+8+2-8-4+1+521)^4 \\
 &:= (-48-3-8+2+8-4+1+521)^4 \\
 &:= (4+8+382+84-1-5-2-1)^4 \\
 &:= (4-8+382+84+1+5+2-1)^4 \\
 &:= (-4+8+382+84+1-5+2+1)^4 \\
 &:= (4-8+382+84-1+5+2+1)^4 \\
 &:= (4+8+3+8+28+415+2+1)^4 \\
 &:= (4+8+3+8+2+8+415+21)^4 \\
 &:= (-4+8+3-8-2-8-41+521)^4 \\
 &:= (-4-8+3+8-2-8-41+521)^4 \\
 &:= (-4-8+3-8-2+8-41+521)^4 \\
 &:= (483-8-28+4+15+2+1)^4 \\
 &:= (483+8+28+4-1-52-1)^4
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 & := (483 + 8 - 2 - 8 + 41 - 52 - 1)^4 & := (492 - 13 - 4 - 2 - 9 - 2 + 8 + 1)^4 \\
 & := (483 - 8 - 2 + 8 + 41 - 52 - 1)^4 & := (492 + 1 - 34 - 2 + 9 - 2 + 8 - 1)^4 \\
 & := (483 + 8 + 2 + 8 + 4 - 15 - 21)^4 & := (492 - 1 - 34 - 2 + 9 - 2 + 8 + 1)^4 \\
 & := (48 + 382 - 8 + 41 + 5 + 2 - 1)^4 & := (49 + 2 - 1 + 3 + 429 - 2 - 8 - 1)^4 \\
 & := (48 + 382 + 8 + 4 + 1 + 5 + 21)^4 & := (49 + 2 + 1 - 3 + 429 + 2 - 8 - 1)^4 \\
 & := (48 + 3 - 8 - 2 - 8 + 415 + 21)^4 & := (49 - 2 - 1 + 3 + 429 + 2 - 8 - 1)^4 \\
 & := (4 + 83 - 8 - 28 + 415 + 2 + 1)^4 & := (49 - 2 + 1 + 3 + 429 - 2 - 8 + 1)^4 \\
 & := (4 - 83 - 8 + 2 - 8 + 41 + 521)^4 & := (49 + 2 - 1 - 3 + 429 + 2 - 8 + 1)^4 \\
 & := (-4 + 8 - 382 + 841 + 5 + 2 - 1)^4 & := (4 + 9 + 21 + 3 + 429 - 2 + 8 - 1)^4 \\
 & := (4 + 8 - 382 + 841 - 5 + 2 + 1)^4 & := (4 + 9 + 21 - 3 + 429 + 2 + 8 + 1)^4 \\
 & := (-4 - 8 + 382 + 84 - 1 - 5 + 21)^4 & := (4 + 9 - 2 + 1 + 3 + 429 + 28 - 1)^4 \\
 & := (4 + 8 + 382 + 8 + 41 + 5 + 21)^4 & := (4 + 9 + 2 + 1 - 3 + 429 + 28 + 1)^4 \\
 & := (-4 + 8 - 3 + 82 - 8 + 415 - 21)^4 & := (4 + 9 - 2 - 1 + 3 + 429 + 28 + 1)^4 \\
 & := (-4 - 8 - 3 + 82 + 8 + 415 - 21)^4 & := (492 + 13 + 4 - 29 - 2 - 8 + 1)^4 \\
 & := (4 + 8 - 3 + 8 - 28 - 41 + 521)^4 & := (492 + 13 + 4 - 2 - 9 - 28 + 1)^4 \\
 & := (483 - 82 + 84 - 15 - 2 + 1)^4 & := (492 - 1 - 3 - 4 - 2 - 92 + 81)^4 \\
 & := (483 + 82 - 84 - 15 + 2 + 1)^4 & := (49 - 21 + 3 + 429 + 2 + 8 + 1)^4 \\
 & := (-48 - 3 + 82 - 84 + 1 + 521)^4 & := (49 - 2 - 1 + 342 + 92 - 8 - 1)^4 \\
 & := (-4 + 83 - 82 - 8 - 41 + 521)^4 & := (4 + 92 + 1 - 3 + 4 + 292 + 81)^4 \\
 & := (4 - 8 + 38 + 284 + 152 - 1)^4 & := (4 - 9 + 21 - 3 + 429 + 28 + 1)^4 \\
 \mathbf{48402200025} & := (4 + 8 - 4 + 0220002 - 5)^2 & := (-4 - 9 - 21 - 3 + 429 - 2 + 81)^4 \\
 & := (-4 + 8 + 4 + 0220002 - 5)^2 & := (492 + 1 + 34 - 29 - 28 + 1)^4 \\
 & := (48 - 40 + 220002 - 5)^2 & := (492 - 1 + 34 + 29 - 2 - 81)^4 \\
 \mathbf{48427561125} & := (-4 - 8 + 4275 - 611 - 2 - 5)^3 & := (49 - 21 + 342 + 92 + 8 + 1)^4 \\
 \mathbf{48627125000} & := (4862 - 712 - 500 + 0)^3 & \mathbf{49221859600} & := (4 - 9 + 221859 + 6 + 00)^2 \\
 \mathbf{48707103808} & := (4 - 870 + 710 + 3808)^3 & \mathbf{49350093632} & := (49 + 3500 + 93 - 6 + 32)^3 \\
 \mathbf{48796810000} & := (487 - 9 - 6 + 8 - 10 + 000)^4 & \mathbf{49382172841} & := (4938 + 217284 - 1)^2 \\
 \mathbf{48827236375} & := (4 + 8 + 8 - 2 + 7 - 2 + 3637 - 5)^3 & \mathbf{49471280711} & := (4947 - 1280 - 7 + 11)^3 \\
 & := (-4 + 8 + 8 + 2 + 7 + 2 + 3637 - 5)^3 & \mathbf{49632710656} & := (496 + 3 - 2 - 7 - 1 - 06 - 5 - 6)^4 \\
 & := (4 + 8 + 8 + 2 - 7 - 2 + 3637 + 5)^3 & & := (496 - 3 + 2 - 7 + 1 - 06 - 5 - 6)^4 \\
 & := (4 + 8 + 8 - 2 - 7 + 2 + 3637 + 5)^3 & & := (496 - 3 - 27 + 1 + 06 + 5 - 6)^4 \\
 & := (4 - 8 - 8 + 27 - 2 + 3637 + 5)^3 & & := (496 - 3 - 27 - 1 + 06 - 5 + 6)^4 \\
 \mathbf{49108313528} & := (49 + 1 + 083 + 1 + 3528)^3 & & := (496 - 3 - 27 + 1 - 06 + 5 + 6)^4 \\
 & := (4 + 91 + 08 + 31 + 3528)^3 & & := (496 - 32 - 7 + 10 + 6 + 5 - 6)^4 \\
 & := (491 + 08 + 3135 + 28)^3 & & := (496 - 32 - 7 + 10 - 6 + 5 + 6)^4 \\
 & := (4 - 9 + 108 + 31 + 3528)^3 & & := (496 + 32 + 7 - 1 - 06 - 56)^4 \\
 \mathbf{49213429281} & := (492 - 13 - 4 - 2 + 9 - 2 - 8 - 1)^4 & & := (496 + 32 - 7 + 1 + 06 - 56)^4 \\
 & := (492 - 13 + 4 + 2 - 9 + 2 - 8 + 1)^4 & & := (496 + 32 - 7 + 10 - 65 + 6)^4
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 & := (4 - 9 + 632 + 7 - 106 - 56)^4 & & := (-50 + 479 - 3 + 049 - 7 + 6)^4 \\
 \mathbf{49673699776} & := (49 + 6 - 7 + 3699 - 77 + 6)^3 & & := (50 + 4 - 7 + 930 - 497 - 6)^4 \\
 \mathbf{49714249733} & := (-497 + 1 + 4249 - 73 - 3)^3 & & \mathbf{50529889873} := (5 - 05298 + 8987 + 3)^3 \\
 \mathbf{49836032000} & := (49 + 8 + 3603 + 20 + 00)^3 & & \mathbf{50906640625} := (5 - 09 + 066 + 406 + 2 + 5)^4 \\
 \mathbf{50039444125} & := (-50 - 0394 + 4 + 4125)^3 & & := (-50 - 90 + 6 + 640 - 6 - 25)^4 \\
 \mathbf{50049003168} & := (50 + 04 + 90 - 03 - 1 + 6 - 8)^5 & & := (-50 - 90 - 6 + 640 + 6 - 25)^4 \\
 & := (50 - 04 + 90 + 03 + 1 + 6 - 8)^5 & & \mathbf{50982270912} := (5 + 0982 + 2709 + 12)^3 \\
 \mathbf{50054665441} & := (500 - 5 + 4 - 6 - 6 - 5 - 4 - 4 - 1)^4 & & \mathbf{51023529829} := (5 + 102 + 3529 + 82 - 9)^3 \\
 & := (500 - 5 - 4 - 6 - 6 - 5 + 4 - 4 - 1)^4 & & \mathbf{51173226225} := (5 - 11 - 7 + 3 + 226225)^2 \\
 & := (500 - 5 - 4 - 6 - 6 - 5 - 4 + 4 - 1)^4 & & := (5 - 1 - 17 + 3 + 226225)^2 \\
 & := (500 + 5 - 4 + 6 + 6 + 5 - 44 - 1)^4 & & \mathbf{51188788097} := (-5118 + 8 + 7 + 8809 + 7)^3 \\
 & := (500 + 5 + 4 + 6 + 6 - 5 - 44 + 1)^4 & & \mathbf{51312965696} := (5 + 1 + 3129 + 6 + 569 + 6)^3 \\
 & := (500 - 5 + 4 + 6 + 6 + 5 - 44 + 1)^4 & & := (51 + 3 + 1 + 2965 + 696)^3 \\
 & := (500 + 5 - 4 + 6 + 6 + 5 - 4 - 41)^4 & & \mathbf{51336683776} := (513 - 36 - 6 + 8 + 3 + 7 - 7 - 6)^4 \\
 & := (50 - 05 + 4 - 6 - 6 - 5 + 441)^4 & & := (513 - 36 - 6 + 8 + 3 - 7 + 7 - 6)^4 \\
 & := (-5 + 0054 - 6 - 6 - 5 + 441)^4 & & := (513 + 3 - 6 - 6 + 8 - 37 + 7 - 6)^4 \\
 & := (5 - 005 - 4 - 66 + 544 - 1)^4 & & := (513 - 3 + 6 + 6 - 8 - 37 - 7 + 6)^4 \\
 & := (-5 + 005 - 4 - 66 + 544 - 1)^4 & & := (5 - 1 + 3 + 366 + 83 + 7 + 7 + 6)^4 \\
 & := (-5 - 005 + 4 - 66 + 544 + 1)^4 & & := (513 + 36 - 68 + 3 - 7 - 7 + 6)^4 \\
 & := (500 + 5 - 4 - 66 - 5 + 44 - 1)^4 & & := (513 - 3 - 66 + 8 + 37 - 7 - 6)^4 \\
 & := (500 - 5 - 4 - 66 + 5 + 44 - 1)^4 & & := (5 - 1 + 336 + 68 - 3 + 77 - 6)^4 \\
 & := (500 - 5 + 4 - 66 - 5 + 44 + 1)^4 & & := (5 + 1 + 336 + 68 - 3 - 7 + 76)^4 \\
 & := (500 - 5 + 4 - 66 - 5 + 4 + 41)^4 & & := (-5 - 1 - 336 - 6 + 837 - 7 - 6)^4 \\
 & := (500 + 5 - 4 - 6 - 65 + 44 - 1)^4 & & := (-5 - 1 + 336 - 6 + 83 - 7 + 76)^4 \\
 & := (500 - 5 + 4 - 6 - 65 + 44 + 1)^4 & & := (5 - 1 - 3 + 36 + 68 + 377 - 6)^4 \\
 & := (500 - 5 + 4 - 6 - 65 + 4 + 41)^4 & & := (5 + 13 - 366 + 837 - 7 - 6)^4 \\
 & := (50 + 05 + 466 - 5 - 44 + 1)^4 & & := (5 - 13 - 366 + 837 + 7 + 6)^4 \\
 & := (50 - 05 + 466 + 5 - 44 + 1)^4 & & := (5 + 1336 - 6 - 83 - 776)^4 \\
 & := (50 - 054 - 66 + 544 - 1)^4 & & \mathbf{51395862232} := (-5 + 1 + 3958 - 6 + 2 - 232)^3 \\
 & & & := (5 + 1395 + 86 + 2232)^3 \\
 \mathbf{50120963703} & := (-50 - 1 + 20 + 9 + 6 + 3703)^3 & & \mathbf{51437343959} := (5 + 1 + 4 + 3734 - 39 + 5 + 9)^3 \\
 \mathbf{50284268371} & := (5 + 02842 + 6 + 837 + 1)^3 & & \mathbf{51520374361} := (5 + 1 + 5 - 2 - 03 + 7 + 43 + 6 - 1)^6 \\
 \mathbf{50366053557} & := (5 + 03660 + 5 + 35 - 5 - 7)^3 & & := (5 + 1 - 5 + 2 + 03 + 7 + 43 + 6 - 1)^6 \\
 & := (5 + 03660 - 5 + 35 + 5 - 7)^3 & & := (-5 + 1 + 5 + 2 + 03 + 7 + 43 + 6 - 1)^6 \\
 & := (-5 + 03660 + 5 + 35 + 5 - 7)^3 & & := (5 + 1 + 5 + 2 + 03 + 7 + 43 - 6 + 1)^6 \\
 & := (50 + 3660 + 5 + 35 - 57)^3 & & := (5 - 1 + 5 - 2 - 03 + 7 + 43 + 6 + 1)^6 \\
 \mathbf{50447927375} & := (-50 + 4479 - 2 - 737 + 5)^3 & & := (5 - 1 - 5 + 2 + 03 + 7 + 43 + 6 + 1)^6 \\
 \mathbf{50479304976} & := (-5 + 04 - 7 + 9 - 30 + 497 + 6)^4 & & := (-5 - 1 + 5 + 2 + 03 + 7 + 43 + 6 + 1)^6 \\
 & := (504 - 7 + 9 + 30 - 49 - 7 - 6)^4 & &
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} &:= (5 - 1 + 5 + 2 + 03 - 7 - 4 - 3 + 61)^6 \\ &:= (5 + 1 - 5 + 2 - 03 + 7 - 4 - 3 + 61)^6 \\ &:= (-5 + 1 + 5 + 2 - 03 + 7 - 4 - 3 + 61)^6 \\ &:= (5 - 1 - 5 - 2 + 03 + 7 - 4 - 3 + 61)^6 \\ &:= (-5 - 1 + 5 - 2 + 03 + 7 - 4 - 3 + 61)^6 \\ &:= (5 + 1 + 5 - 2 - 03 - 7 + 4 - 3 + 61)^6 \\ &:= (5 + 1 - 5 + 2 + 03 - 7 + 4 - 3 + 61)^6 \\ &:= (-5 + 1 + 5 + 2 + 03 - 7 + 4 - 3 + 61)^6 \\ &:= (-5 + 1 - 5 - 2 + 03 + 7 + 4 - 3 + 61)^6 \\ &:= (5 - 1 + 5 + 2 - 03 - 7 - 4 + 3 + 61)^6 \\ &:= (5 - 1 - 5 - 2 - 03 + 7 - 4 + 3 + 61)^6 \\ &:= (-5 - 1 + 5 - 2 - 03 + 7 - 4 + 3 + 61)^6 \\ &:= (-5 - 1 - 5 + 2 + 03 + 7 - 4 + 3 + 61)^6 \\ &:= (5 + 1 - 5 + 2 - 03 - 7 + 4 + 3 + 61)^6 \\ &:= (-5 + 1 + 5 + 2 - 03 - 7 + 4 + 3 + 61)^6 \\ &:= (5 - 1 - 5 - 2 + 03 - 7 + 4 + 3 + 61)^6 \\ &:= (-5 - 1 + 5 - 2 + 03 - 7 + 4 + 3 + 61)^6 \\ &:= (-5 + 1 - 5 - 2 - 03 + 7 + 4 + 3 + 61)^6 \\ &:= (5 + 15 - 2 + 037 + 4 - 3 + 6 - 1)^6 \\ &:= (-5 + 15 + 2 + 037 + 4 + 3 + 6 - 1)^6 \\ &:= (5 + 15 + 2 + 037 + 4 + 3 - 6 + 1)^6 \\ &:= (5 + 15 - 2 + 037 - 4 + 3 + 6 + 1)^6 \\ &:= (5 - 15 - 2 + 03 + 74 + 3 - 6 - 1)^6 \\ &:= (5 - 15 - 2 - 03 + 74 - 3 + 6 - 1)^6 \\ &:= (-5 - 15 + 2 + 03 + 74 - 3 + 6 - 1)^6 \\ &:= (-5 - 15 + 2 - 03 + 74 + 3 + 6 - 1)^6 \\ &:= (5 - 15 + 2 + 03 + 74 - 3 - 6 + 1)^6 \\ &:= (5 - 15 + 2 - 03 + 74 + 3 - 6 + 1)^6 \\ &:= (5 + 15 - 2 - 03 + 7 + 4 + 36 - 1)^6 \\ &:= (-5 + 15 + 2 + 03 + 7 + 4 + 36 - 1)^6 \\ &:= (5 + 15 - 2 + 03 + 7 - 4 + 36 + 1)^6 \\ &:= (5 - 1 + 5 + 20 + 3 - 7 + 43 - 6 - 1)^6 \\ &:= (5 + 1 - 5 + 20 - 3 + 7 + 43 - 6 - 1)^6 \\ &:= (-5 + 1 + 5 + 20 - 3 + 7 + 43 - 6 - 1)^6 \\ &:= (-5 - 1 - 5 + 20 - 3 + 7 + 43 + 6 - 1)^6 \\ &:= (5 - 1 - 5 + 20 - 3 + 7 + 43 - 6 + 1)^6 \\ &:= (-5 - 1 + 5 + 20 - 3 + 7 + 43 - 6 + 1)^6 \\ &:= (5 + 1 - 5 + 20 - 3 - 7 + 43 + 6 + 1)^6 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} &:= (-5 + 1 + 5 + 20 - 3 - 7 + 43 + 6 + 1)^6 \\ &:= (-5 + 1 - 5 + 20 + 3 - 7 - 4 - 3 + 61)^6 \\ &:= (-5 - 1 - 5 + 20 - 3 - 7 + 4 - 3 + 61)^6 \\ &:= (5 - 1 + 5 - 20 + 3 + 7 + 4 - 3 + 61)^6 \\ &:= (-5 + 1 - 5 + 20 - 3 - 7 - 4 + 3 + 61)^6 \\ &:= (5 + 1 + 5 - 20 + 3 + 7 - 4 + 3 + 61)^6 \\ &:= (5 - 1 + 5 - 20 - 3 + 7 + 4 + 3 + 61)^6 \\ &:= (-5 + 1 - 5 + 2 + 037 - 4 + 36 - 1)^6 \\ &:= (-5 - 1 - 5 + 2 + 037 - 4 + 36 + 1)^6 \\ &:= (51 + 52 + 03 - 7 - 43 + 6 - 1)^6 \\ &:= (-51 + 52 + 03 + 7 + 43 + 6 + 1)^6 \\ &:= (51 - 5 - 20 + 37 - 4 - 3 + 6 - 1)^6 \\ &:= (51 + 5 - 20 + 37 - 4 - 3 - 6 + 1)^6 \\ &:= (-51 + 5 + 20 + 3 + 74 + 3 + 6 + 1)^6 \\ &:= (51 - 5 - 20 - 3 + 7 - 4 + 36 - 1)^6 \\ &:= (51 - 5 - 20 + 3 - 7 + 4 + 36 - 1)^6 \\ &:= (51 - 5 + 2 - 037 + 43 + 6 + 1)^6 \\ &:= (51 - 5 - 2 - 037 - 4 - 3 + 61)^6 \\ &:= (-51 + 5 + 2 + 037 + 4 + 3 + 61)^6 \\ &:= (51 + 5 - 2 - 03 + 74 - 3 - 61)^6 \\ &:= (51 - 5 + 2 + 03 + 74 - 3 - 61)^6 \\ &:= (51 - 5 + 2 - 03 + 74 + 3 - 61)^6 \\ &:= (-5 + 15 + 20 + 37 + 4 - 3 - 6 - 1)^6 \\ &:= (-5 + 15 + 20 + 37 - 4 + 3 - 6 + 1)^6 \\ &:= (5 - 15 + 20 + 37 + 4 + 3 + 6 + 1)^6 \\ &:= (5 + 15 - 20 - 3 + 74 - 3 - 6 - 1)^6 \\ &:= (-5 - 15 + 20 - 3 + 74 - 3 - 6 - 1)^6 \\ &:= (5 + 15 + 20 - 3 - 7 - 4 + 36 - 1)^6 \\ &:= (-5 + 15 + 20 - 3 - 7 + 4 + 36 + 1)^6 \\ &:= (5 - 15 + 20 + 3 + 7 + 4 + 36 + 1)^6 \\ &:= (5 - 15 - 2 + 037 + 43 - 6 - 1)^6 \\ &:= (-5 + 1 + 52 - 037 + 43 + 6 + 1)^6 \\ &:= (-5 + 1 + 52 + 03 + 74 - 3 - 61)^6 \\ &:= (-5 + 1 + 52 - 03 + 74 + 3 - 61)^6 \\ &:= (5 + 1 + 5 - 20 + 37 - 4 + 36 + 1)^6 \\ &:= (5 + 1 - 5 + 20 + 3 + 74 - 36 - 1)^6 \\ &:= (-5 + 1 + 5 + 20 + 3 + 74 - 36 - 1)^6 \\ &:= (5 - 1 - 5 + 20 + 3 + 74 - 36 + 1)^6 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 & := (-5 - 1 + 5 + 20 + 3 + 74 - 36 + 1)^6 & := (-5 - 1 - 7 + 69 + 4 + 458 - 41)^4 \\
 & := (51 + 52 - 03 - 74 + 36 - 1)^6 & := (-517 + 6 + 944 - 5 + 8 + 41)^4 \\
 & := (-51 + 5 + 20 + 37 + 43 + 6 + 1)^6 & := (517 - 6 + 94 - 45 - 84 + 1)^4 \\
 & := (51 + 5 - 20 - 37 + 4 - 3 + 61)^6 & := (517 + 6 + 9 + 44 - 58 - 41)^4 \\
 & := (-51 - 5 + 20 + 37 - 4 + 3 + 61)^6 & := (-5 + 17 + 69 + 445 - 8 - 41)^4 \\
 & := (5 - 15 - 20 + 37 - 4 - 3 + 61)^6 & := (-5 + 1 + 76 - 94 + 458 + 41)^4 \\
 & := (-5 + 15 + 20 - 37 + 4 + 3 + 61)^6 & := (-5 + 1 + 76 + 9 - 445 + 841)^4 \\
 & := (-5 + 1 - 5 - 20 + 3743 + 6 + 1)^3 & := (-5 + 17 + 69 - 445 + 841)^4 \\
 & := (51 - 5 + 2 + 0374 - 361)^6 & \mathbf{51853389489} := (5 + 1 - 85 + 3 + 3894 - 89)^3 \\
 & := (5 - 15 + 203 - 74 + 3 - 61)^6 & := (-5 - 18 - 53 + 3894 - 89)^3 \\
 & := (-5 + 1 + 52 + 0374 - 361)^6 & \mathbf{51888844699} := (5 + 1 + 8 + 8 + 8 + 8 + 4 + 4 - 6 + 99)^5 \\
 & := (515 + 20 - 37 - 436 - 1)^6 & := (-5 - 1 + 8 + 8 + 8 + 8 + 4 + 4 + 6 + 99)^5 \\
 \mathbf{51686703125} & := (516 + 8 + 6 + 70 + 3125)^3 & := (51 + 88 + 8 + 8 + 4 + 4 - 6 - 9 - 9)^5 \\
 \mathbf{51769445841} & := (5 + 1 + 7 + 6 + 9 - 4 + 458 - 4 - 1)^4 & := (51 + 88 - 8 - 8 - 4 - 4 + 6 + 9 + 9)^5 \\
 & := (5 - 1 - 7 + 6 + 9 + 4 + 458 + 4 - 1)^4 & := (51 + 8 + 88 + 8 + 4 + 4 - 6 - 9 - 9)^5 \\
 & := (5 - 1 + 7 + 6 + 9 - 4 + 458 - 4 + 1)^4 & := (51 - 8 + 88 - 8 - 4 - 4 + 6 + 9 + 9)^5 \\
 & := (-5 + 1 + 7 + 6 + 9 + 4 + 458 - 4 + 1)^4 & := (51 + 8 + 8 + 88 + 4 + 4 - 6 - 9 - 9)^5 \\
 & := (-5 + 1 + 7 + 6 + 9 - 4 + 458 + 4 + 1)^4 & := (51 - 8 - 8 + 88 - 4 - 4 + 6 + 9 + 9)^5 \\
 & := (5 + 1 + 7 + 6 - 9 + 4 + 458 + 4 + 1)^4 & := (51 + 8 + 8 + 8 + 84 + 4 - 6 - 9 - 9)^5 \\
 & := (517 + 6 + 9 + 4 + 4 - 58 - 4 - 1)^4 & := (51 - 8 - 8 - 8 + 84 + 4 + 6 + 9 + 9)^5 \\
 & := (517 + 6 + 9 + 4 - 4 - 58 + 4 - 1)^4 & := (51 + 8 + 8 + 8 + 8 + 44 - 6 + 9 + 9)^5 \\
 & := (517 + 6 + 9 - 4 + 4 - 58 + 4 - 1)^4 & := (5 + 18 + 88 + 8 + 4 + 4 - 6 + 9 + 9)^5 \\
 & := (51 - 7 - 6 - 9 + 445 + 8 - 4 - 1)^4 & := (5 + 18 + 8 + 88 + 4 + 4 - 6 + 9 + 9)^5 \\
 & := (51 + 7 - 6 - 9 + 445 - 8 - 4 + 1)^4 & := (5 + 18 + 8 + 8 + 84 + 4 - 6 + 9 + 9)^5 \\
 & := (5 + 17 + 6 + 9 + 445 - 8 + 4 - 1)^4 & := (5 + 1 + 8 - 8 - 8 - 8 + 44 + 6 + 99)^5 \\
 & := (-5 + 17 + 6 + 9 + 445 + 8 - 4 + 1)^4 & := (5 + 1 - 8 + 8 - 8 - 8 + 44 + 6 + 99)^5 \\
 & := (5 + 17 + 6 - 9 + 445 + 8 + 4 + 1)^4 & := (5 + 1 - 8 - 8 + 8 - 8 + 44 + 6 + 99)^5 \\
 & := (5 - 1 - 7 - 6 - 9 - 4 + 458 + 41)^4 & := (5 + 1 - 8 - 8 - 8 + 8 + 44 + 6 + 99)^5 \\
 & := (-5 + 1 - 7 - 6 - 9 + 4 + 458 + 41)^4 & := (5 + 1 + 8 - 8 - 8 - 8 + 4 + 46 + 99)^5 \\
 & := (517 + 6 - 94 + 45 + 8 - 4 - 1)^4 & := (5 + 1 - 8 + 8 - 8 - 8 + 4 + 46 + 99)^5 \\
 & := (517 + 6 - 94 + 4 - 5 + 8 + 41)^4 & := (5 + 1 - 8 - 8 + 8 - 8 + 4 + 46 + 99)^5 \\
 & := (517 - 6 - 9 - 4 - 4 - 58 + 41)^4 & := (5 + 1 - 8 - 8 - 8 + 8 + 4 + 46 + 99)^5 \\
 & := (-5 - 17 + 6 - 94 + 4 + 584 - 1)^4 & := (-51 + 88 + 88 + 4 + 4 + 6 + 9 - 9)^5 \\
 & := (5 - 17 - 6 - 94 + 4 + 584 + 1)^4 & := (-51 + 88 + 88 + 4 + 4 + 6 - 9 + 9)^5 \\
 & := (5 + 1 - 76 + 94 + 458 - 4 - 1)^4 & := (-51 + 88 + 8 + 84 + 4 + 6 + 9 - 9)^5 \\
 & := (5 - 1 - 76 + 94 + 458 - 4 + 1)^4 & := (-51 + 88 + 8 + 84 + 4 + 6 - 9 + 9)^5 \\
 & := (-5 + 1 - 76 + 94 + 458 + 4 + 1)^4 & := (-51 + 88 + 8 + 8 + 4 + 4 + 69 + 9)^5 \\
 & := (-5 + 1 + 76 + 9 + 445 - 8 - 41)^4 & := (-51 + 8 + 88 + 84 + 4 + 6 + 9 - 9)^5
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 & := (-51 + 8 + 88 + 84 + 4 + 6 - 9 + 9)^5 & := (51 - 8 - 8 + 88 - 44 + 69 - 9)^5 \\
 & := (-51 + 8 + 88 + 8 + 4 + 4 + 69 + 9)^5 & := (51 + 8 + 8 + 88 + 44 - 69 + 9)^5 \\
 & := (-51 + 8 + 8 + 88 + 4 + 4 + 69 + 9)^5 & := (-5 + 18 + 88 + 84 - 46 + 9 - 9)^5 \\
 & := (51 - 8 - 8 - 8 + 84 + 46 - 9 - 9)^5 & := (-5 + 18 + 88 + 84 - 46 - 9 + 9)^5 \\
 & := (-51 + 8 + 8 + 8 + 84 + 4 + 69 + 9)^5 & := (5 + 18 + 88 + 84 + 4 - 69 + 9)^5 \\
 & := (51 + 8 - 8 - 8 - 8 + 44 + 69 - 9)^5 & := (5 + 1 - 88 - 8 + 84 + 46 + 99)^5 \\
 & := (51 - 8 + 8 - 8 - 8 + 44 + 69 - 9)^5 & := (5 + 1 - 8 - 88 + 84 + 46 + 99)^5 \\
 & := (51 - 8 - 8 + 8 - 8 + 44 + 69 - 9)^5 & := (5 + 188 - 88 - 44 + 69 + 9)^5 \\
 & := (51 - 8 - 8 - 8 + 8 + 44 + 69 - 9)^5 & \mathbf{51936866891} := (-5 + 1 - 9 + 3686 + 68 - 9 - 1)^3 \\
 & := (5 + 188 - 8 - 8 - 44 + 6 + 9 - 9)^5 & := (-5 - 1 - 9 + 3686 + 68 - 9 + 1)^3 \\
 & := (5 + 188 - 8 - 8 - 44 + 6 - 9 + 9)^5 & := (-51 - 9 + 3686 + 6 + 8 + 91)^3 \\
 & := (-5 + 188 + 8 + 8 + 4 - 46 - 9 - 9)^5 & \mathbf{52187836553} := (5 + 2 - 1 + 87 - 8 + 3655 - 3)^3 \\
 & := (5 + 188 + 8 + 8 + 4 + 4 - 69 - 9)^5 & := (52 + 18 + 7 + 8 + 3655 - 3)^3 \\
 & := (-5 + 188 + 8 + 8 + 4 - 4 - 69 + 9)^5 & := (5 - 21 + 87 + 8 + 3655 + 3)^3 \\
 & := (-5 + 188 + 8 + 8 - 4 + 4 - 69 + 9)^5 & \mathbf{52204938256} := (522 + 04 - 9 - 38 - 2 - 5 + 6)^4 \\
 & := (5 - 18 + 88 + 84 + 4 - 6 - 9 - 9)^5 & := (522 - 04 + 9 - 3 + 8 + 2 - 56)^4 \\
 & := (-5 - 18 + 88 + 84 - 4 - 6 + 9 - 9)^5 & := (522 + 04 + 9 - 38 - 25 + 6)^4 \\
 & := (-5 - 18 + 88 + 84 - 4 - 6 - 9 + 9)^5 & := (-52 + 20 + 493 + 8 - 2 + 5 + 6)^4 \\
 & := (5 + 18 + 88 + 8 + 44 - 6 - 9 - 9)^5 & := (52 + 20 + 4 + 9 + 382 + 5 + 6)^4 \\
 & := (5 - 18 + 88 + 8 + 44 - 6 + 9 + 9)^5 & := (-52 - 2 + 0493 + 8 + 25 + 6)^4 \\
 & := (5 + 18 + 8 + 88 + 44 - 6 - 9 - 9)^5 & := (5 + 22 + 04 + 9 + 382 + 56)^4 \\
 & := (5 - 18 + 8 + 88 + 44 - 6 + 9 + 9)^5 & := (5 + 2 + 20 + 4 + 9 + 382 + 56)^4 \\
 & := (5 + 1 + 88 - 8 - 8 - 44 + 6 + 99)^5 & := (-5 - 2 - 2 + 049 + 382 + 56)^4 \\
 & := (-5 - 1 + 88 + 8 - 8 + 4 - 46 + 99)^5 & := (-522 + 04 + 938 + 2 + 56)^4 \\
 & := (-5 - 1 + 88 - 8 + 8 + 4 - 46 + 99)^5 & \mathbf{52287224896} := (5 + 228722 - 48 - 9 - 6)^2 \\
 & := (5 + 1 - 8 + 88 - 8 - 44 + 6 + 99)^5 & \mathbf{52313624000} := (5 - 231 - 36 + 2 + 4000)^3 \\
 & := (-5 - 1 + 8 + 88 - 8 + 4 - 46 + 99)^5 & \mathbf{52397594488} := (5 + 2 - 3 + 9 - 759 + 4488)^3 \\
 & := (-5 - 1 - 8 + 88 + 8 + 4 - 46 + 99)^5 & := (52 - 39 - 759 + 4488)^3 \\
 & := (5 + 1 - 8 - 8 + 88 - 44 + 6 + 99)^5 & \mathbf{52523350144} := (5 + 2 + 5 + 2 + 3 + 3 + 5 + 01 + 4 + 4)^7 \\
 & := (-5 - 1 + 8 - 8 + 88 + 4 - 46 + 99)^5 & := (5 + 25 + 2 + 3 + 3 + 5 - 01 - 4 - 4)^7 \\
 & := (-5 - 1 - 8 + 8 + 88 + 4 - 46 + 99)^5 & := (5 + 25 + 2 + 3 + 3 - 5 + 01 + 4 - 4)^7 \\
 & := (-5 - 1 + 8 + 8 - 8 + 84 - 46 + 99)^5 & := (5 + 25 - 2 + 3 - 3 + 5 + 01 + 4 - 4)^7 \\
 & := (-5 - 1 + 8 - 8 + 8 + 84 - 46 + 99)^5 & := (5 + 25 - 2 - 3 + 3 + 5 + 01 + 4 - 4)^7 \\
 & := (-5 - 1 - 8 + 8 + 8 + 84 - 46 + 99)^5 & := (-5 + 25 + 2 + 3 + 3 + 5 + 01 + 4 - 4)^7 \\
 & := (51 + 88 - 8 - 8 - 44 + 69 - 9)^5 & := (5 + 25 + 2 + 3 + 3 - 5 + 01 - 4 + 4)^7 \\
 & := (51 + 88 + 8 + 8 + 44 - 69 + 9)^5 & := (5 + 25 - 2 + 3 - 3 + 5 + 01 - 4 + 4)^7 \\
 & := (51 - 8 + 88 - 8 - 44 + 69 - 9)^5 & := (5 + 25 - 2 - 3 + 3 + 5 + 01 - 4 + 4)^7 \\
 & := (51 + 8 + 88 + 8 + 44 - 69 + 9)^5 & := (-5 + 25 + 2 + 3 + 3 + 5 + 01 - 4 + 4)^7
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} &:= (5 + 25 + 2 + 3 - 3 - 5 - 01 + 4 + 4)^7 & &:= (52 - 5 - 2 - 3 - 3 + 5 - 014 + 4)^7 \\ &:= (5 + 25 + 2 - 3 + 3 - 5 - 01 + 4 + 4)^7 & &:= (-5 + 25 + 23 + 3 - 5 + 01 - 4 - 4)^7 \\ &:= (5 + 25 - 2 - 3 - 3 + 5 - 01 + 4 + 4)^7 & &:= (-5 + 25 + 23 - 3 - 5 - 01 + 4 - 4)^7 \\ &:= (-5 + 25 + 2 + 3 - 3 + 5 - 01 + 4 + 4)^7 & &:= (-5 + 25 + 23 - 3 - 5 - 01 - 4 + 4)^7 \\ &:= (-5 + 25 + 2 - 3 + 3 + 5 - 01 + 4 + 4)^7 & &:= (5 - 25 - 2 + 3 + 3 + 5 + 01 + 44)^7 \\ &:= (5 + 2 + 5 + 23 + 3 + 5 - 01 - 4 - 4)^7 & &:= (5 - 2 + 52 - 33 + 5 - 01 + 4 + 4)^7 \\ &:= (5 + 2 + 5 + 23 + 3 - 5 + 01 + 4 - 4)^7 & &:= (5 + 2 + 52 + 3 - 35 - 01 + 4 + 4)^7 \\ &:= (5 - 2 + 5 + 23 - 3 + 5 + 01 + 4 - 4)^7 & &:= (5 - 2 + 52 - 3 - 3 - 5 - 014 + 4)^7 \\ &:= (5 + 2 - 5 + 23 + 3 + 5 + 01 + 4 - 4)^7 & &:= (-5 + 2 + 52 + 3 - 3 - 5 - 014 + 4)^7 \\ &:= (-5 + 2 + 5 + 23 + 3 + 5 + 01 + 4 - 4)^7 & &:= (-5 + 2 + 52 - 3 + 3 - 5 - 014 + 4)^7 \\ &:= (5 + 2 + 5 + 23 + 3 - 5 + 01 - 4 + 4)^7 & &:= (-5 - 2 + 52 - 3 - 3 + 5 - 014 + 4)^7 \\ &:= (5 - 2 + 5 + 23 - 3 + 5 + 01 - 4 + 4)^7 & &:= (5 + 2 + 5 - 23 - 3 + 5 - 01 + 44)^7 \\ &:= (5 + 2 - 5 + 23 + 3 + 5 + 01 - 4 + 4)^7 & &:= (5 + 2 + 5 - 2 - 33 + 50 - 1 + 4 + 4)^7 \\ &:= (-5 + 2 + 5 + 23 + 3 + 5 + 01 - 4 + 4)^7 & &:= (5 - 2 + 5 + 2 - 33 + 50 - 1 + 4 + 4)^7 \\ &:= (5 + 2 + 5 + 23 - 3 - 5 - 01 + 4 + 4)^7 & &:= (5 + 2 + 5 + 2 + 33 + 5 - 014 - 4)^7 \\ &:= (5 + 2 - 5 + 23 - 3 + 5 - 01 + 4 + 4)^7 & &:= (5 - 2 - 5 - 2 + 33 - 5 + 014 - 4)^7 \\ &:= (-5 + 2 + 5 + 23 - 3 + 5 - 01 + 4 + 4)^7 & &:= (-5 - 2 + 5 - 2 + 33 - 5 + 014 - 4)^7 \\ &:= (5 - 2 - 5 - 2 + 3 - 3 - 5 - 01 + 44)^7 & &:= (-5 - 2 - 5 - 2 + 33 + 5 + 014 - 4)^7 \\ &:= (-5 - 2 + 5 - 2 + 3 - 3 - 5 - 01 + 44)^7 & &:= (5 - 2 + 5 - 2 + 33 + 5 - 014 + 4)^7 \\ &:= (5 - 2 - 5 - 2 - 3 + 3 - 5 - 01 + 44)^7 & &:= (5 + 2 + 5 + 2 + 3 + 35 - 014 - 4)^7 \\ &:= (-5 - 2 + 5 - 2 - 3 + 3 - 5 - 01 + 44)^7 & &:= (-5 - 2 - 5 - 2 + 3 + 35 + 014 - 4)^7 \\ &:= (-5 + 2 - 5 - 2 + 3 + 3 - 5 - 01 + 44)^7 & &:= (5 - 2 + 5 - 2 + 3 + 35 - 014 + 4)^7 \\ &:= (-5 - 2 - 5 + 2 + 3 + 3 - 5 - 01 + 44)^7 & &:= (5 - 2 - 5 - 2 + 3 + 3 + 50 - 14 - 4)^7 \\ &:= (-5 - 2 - 5 - 2 + 3 - 3 + 5 - 01 + 44)^7 & &:= (-5 - 2 + 5 - 2 + 3 + 3 + 50 - 14 - 4)^7 \\ &:= (-5 - 2 - 5 - 2 - 3 + 3 + 5 - 01 + 44)^7 & &:= (5 + 2 - 5 - 2 - 3 - 3 + 50 - 14 + 4)^7 \\ &:= (5 + 2 - 5 - 2 - 3 - 3 - 5 + 01 + 44)^7 & &:= (-5 + 2 + 5 - 2 - 3 - 3 + 50 - 14 + 4)^7 \\ &:= (-5 + 2 + 5 - 2 - 3 - 3 - 5 + 01 + 44)^7 & &:= (5 - 2 - 5 + 2 - 3 - 3 + 50 - 14 + 4)^7 \\ &:= (5 - 2 - 5 + 2 - 3 - 3 - 5 + 01 + 44)^7 & &:= (-5 - 2 + 5 + 2 - 3 - 3 + 50 - 14 + 4)^7 \\ &:= (-5 - 2 + 5 + 2 - 3 - 3 - 5 + 01 + 44)^7 & &:= (-5 + 2 - 5 + 2 + 3 - 3 + 50 - 14 + 4)^7 \\ &:= (-5 + 2 - 5 + 2 + 3 - 3 - 5 + 01 + 44)^7 & &:= (-5 + 2 - 5 + 2 - 3 + 3 + 50 - 14 + 4)^7 \\ &:= (-5 + 2 - 5 + 2 - 3 + 3 - 5 + 01 + 44)^7 & &:= (52 - 52 - 3 - 3 - 5 + 01 + 44)^7 \\ &:= (-5 + 2 - 5 - 2 - 3 - 3 + 5 + 01 + 44)^7 & &:= (-52 + 52 - 3 - 3 - 5 + 01 + 44)^7 \\ &:= (-5 - 2 - 5 + 2 - 3 - 3 + 5 + 01 + 44)^7 & &:= (52 - 5 + 23 - 35 - 01 + 4 - 4)^7 \\ &:= (52 + 5 - 2 - 33 + 5 - 01 + 4 + 4)^7 & &:= (52 - 5 + 23 - 35 - 01 - 4 + 4)^7 \\ &:= (52 + 5 + 2 + 3 - 35 - 01 + 4 + 4)^7 & &:= (52 + 5 + 23 + 3 - 50 + 1 + 4 - 4)^7 \\ &:= (52 + 5 - 2 - 3 - 3 - 5 - 014 + 4)^7 & &:= (52 + 5 + 23 + 3 - 50 + 1 - 4 + 4)^7 \\ &:= (52 - 5 + 2 + 3 - 3 - 5 - 014 + 4)^7 & &:= (52 + 5 + 23 - 3 - 50 - 1 + 4 + 4)^7 \\ &:= (52 - 5 + 2 - 3 + 3 - 5 - 014 + 4)^7 & &:= (52 - 5 - 23 - 3 - 5 + 014 + 4)^7 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 &:= (52 - 5 + 2 + 33 - 5 + 01 - 44)^7 & &:= (-5 - 25 + 2 - 33 + 50 + 1 + 44)^7 \\
 &:= (-52 + 5 - 2 + 33 + 5 + 01 + 44)^7 & &:= (5 + 2 + 523 - 3 - 501 + 4 + 4)^7 \\
 &:= (52 - 5 - 2 - 3 + 35 + 01 - 44)^7 & &:= (-5 - 2 - 52 + 33 + 50 + 14 - 4)^7 \\
 &:= (-52 + 5 - 2 + 3 + 35 + 01 + 44)^7 & & \mathbf{52523718625} := (5 + 2 + 5 + 2 + 3718 + 6 + 2 + 5)^3 \\
 &:= (-52 - 5 - 2 + 3 - 3 + 50 - 1 + 44)^7 & &:= (5 + 25 - 2 + 3718 + 6 - 2 - 5)^3 \\
 &:= (-52 - 5 - 2 - 3 + 3 + 50 - 1 + 44)^7 & &:= (-5 + 25 - 2 + 3718 + 6 - 2 + 5)^3 \\
 &:= (52 - 5 - 2 - 3 - 3 - 50 + 1 + 44)^7 & &:= (5 - 2 - 5 - 2 + 3718 + 6 + 25)^3 \\
 &:= (-52 - 5 + 2 - 3 - 3 + 50 + 1 + 44)^7 & &:= (-5 - 2 + 5 - 2 + 3718 + 6 + 25)^3 \\
 &:= (-5 - 25 + 23 + 3 - 5 - 01 + 44)^7 & & \mathbf{52607913723} := (5 - 2 + 6 + 07 + 9 - 1 + 3723)^3 \\
 &:= (-5 + 25 - 23 - 3 - 5 + 01 + 44)^7 & &:= (-5 + 26 - 07 + 9 + 1 + 3723)^3 \\
 &:= (-5 + 25 - 2 - 33 + 50 - 1 + 4 - 4)^7 & & \mathbf{52643172481} := (5 - 2 + 6 - 4 + 3 - 1 - 7 - 2 + 481)^4 \\
 &:= (-5 + 25 - 2 - 33 + 50 - 1 - 4 + 4)^7 & &:= (5 + 2 - 6 + 4 + 3 - 1 - 7 - 2 + 481)^4 \\
 &:= (5 - 25 - 2 + 33 + 5 + 014 + 4)^7 & &:= (5 + 2 + 6 - 4 - 3 + 1 - 7 - 2 + 481)^4 \\
 &:= (5 - 25 - 2 + 3 + 35 + 014 + 4)^7 & &:= (-5 - 2 + 6 + 4 + 3 + 1 - 7 - 2 + 481)^4 \\
 &:= (-5 - 25 - 2 + 3 + 3 + 50 + 14 - 4)^7 & &:= (5 + 2 - 6 - 4 - 3 - 1 + 7 - 2 + 481)^4 \\
 &:= (-5 - 25 + 2 - 3 - 3 + 50 + 14 + 4)^7 & &:= (-5 - 2 - 6 + 4 + 3 - 1 + 7 - 2 + 481)^4 \\
 &:= (-5 + 2 + 52 + 33 - 5 + 01 - 44)^7 & &:= (-5 - 2 + 6 - 4 - 3 + 1 + 7 - 2 + 481)^4 \\
 &:= (5 - 2 - 52 + 33 + 5 + 01 + 44)^7 & &:= (-5 + 2 - 6 + 4 - 3 + 1 + 7 - 2 + 481)^4 \\
 &:= (-5 - 2 + 52 - 3 + 35 + 01 - 44)^7 & &:= (-5 + 2 + 6 + 4 - 3 - 1 - 7 + 2 + 481)^4 \\
 &:= (5 - 2 - 52 + 3 + 35 + 01 + 44)^7 & &:= (5 - 2 - 6 + 4 + 3 - 1 - 7 + 2 + 481)^4 \\
 &:= (-5 - 2 - 52 + 3 - 3 + 50 - 1 + 44)^7 & &:= (5 - 2 + 6 - 4 - 3 + 1 - 7 + 2 + 481)^4 \\
 &:= (-5 - 2 - 52 - 3 + 3 + 50 - 1 + 44)^7 & &:= (5 + 2 - 6 + 4 - 3 + 1 - 7 + 2 + 481)^4 \\
 &:= (-5 - 2 + 52 - 3 - 3 - 50 + 1 + 44)^7 & &:= (-5 + 2 + 6 - 4 + 3 + 1 - 7 + 2 + 481)^4 \\
 &:= (-5 + 2 - 52 - 3 - 3 + 50 + 1 + 44)^7 & &:= (5 - 2 - 6 - 4 - 3 - 1 + 7 + 2 + 481)^4 \\
 &:= (5 + 2 + 5 - 23 + 35 + 014 - 4)^7 & &:= (-5 + 2 - 6 - 4 + 3 - 1 + 7 + 2 + 481)^4 \\
 &:= (-5 + 2 - 5 - 23 - 3 + 50 + 14 + 4)^7 & &:= (-5 - 2 - 6 + 4 - 3 + 1 + 7 + 2 + 481)^4 \\
 &:= (5 - 2 - 5 - 2 + 33 + 50 - 1 - 44)^7 & &:= (526 + 4 - 31 - 7 - 2 - 4 - 8 + 1)^4 \\
 &:= (-5 - 2 + 5 - 2 + 33 + 50 - 1 - 44)^7 & &:= (526 - 4 - 31 - 7 - 2 + 4 - 8 + 1)^4 \\
 &:= (-5 + 2 - 5 + 2 + 33 + 50 + 1 - 44)^7 & &:= (52 + 6 + 431 - 7 + 2 + 4 - 8 - 1)^4 \\
 &:= (5 - 2 + 5 - 2 + 33 - 50 + 1 + 44)^7 & &:= (52 - 6 + 431 - 7 - 2 + 4 + 8 - 1)^4 \\
 &:= (525 + 2 + 3 - 3 - 501 + 4 + 4)^7 & &:= (52 - 6 + 431 + 7 - 2 + 4 - 8 + 1)^4 \\
 &:= (525 + 2 - 3 + 3 - 501 + 4 + 4)^7 & &:= (-5 - 2 - 6 + 431 + 72 - 4 - 8 + 1)^4 \\
 &:= (52 - 52 - 3 - 3 + 50 - 14 + 4)^7 & &:= (526 - 43 - 17 + 2 + 4 + 8 - 1)^4 \\
 &:= (-52 + 52 - 3 - 3 + 50 - 14 + 4)^7 & &:= (526 + 4 + 31 - 7 + 2 + 4 - 81)^4 \\
 &:= (52 - 5 - 23 - 35 + 01 + 44)^7 & &:= (526 + 4 - 3 - 17 - 24 - 8 + 1)^4 \\
 &:= (52 - 5 - 23 + 3 + 50 + 1 - 44)^7 & &:= (52 + 6 + 431 + 7 - 24 + 8 - 1)^4 \\
 &:= (-52 - 5 - 2 + 33 + 50 + 14 - 4)^7 & &:= (-52 + 6 + 431 + 7 + 2 + 4 + 81)^4 \\
 &:= (-5 + 25 - 23 - 3 + 50 - 14 + 4)^7 & &:= (-52 + 6 + 4 + 31 + 7 + 2 + 481)^4
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 &:= (5 - 26 + 431 + 72 + 4 - 8 + 1)^4 \\
 &:= (5 + 26 - 43 + 1 + 7 + 2 + 481)^4 \\
 &:= (-5 + 2 + 643 - 172 + 4 + 8 - 1)^4 \\
 &:= (5 - 2 + 643 - 172 - 4 + 8 + 1)^4 \\
 &:= (526 - 43 + 1 + 72 + 4 - 81)^4 \\
 &:= (526 - 4 - 3 + 17 + 24 - 81)^4 \\
 &:= (-5 - 264 + 31 + 724 - 8 + 1)^4 \\
 &:= (-5 - 2 + 64 + 317 + 24 + 81)^4 \\
 \mathbf{52861038777} &:= (5 + 2861 + 03 + 877 + 7)^3 \\
 \mathbf{52902300025} &:= (5 + 2 - 9 + 0230002 + 5)^2 \\
 \mathbf{52945593875} &:= (-5 - 2 - 94 - 5 - 5 - 9 + 3875)^3 \\
 &:= (-52 - 9 - 45 - 5 - 9 + 3875)^3 \\
 &:= (-5 - 2 - 9 - 45 - 59 + 3875)^3 \\
 \mathbf{52987905216} &:= (-5298 + 7 + 9052 + 1 - 6)^3 \\
 \mathbf{53084160000} &:= (-5 - 30 - 84 - 1 + 600 + 00)^4 \\
 \mathbf{53157376000} &:= (-5 - 3 + 15 - 7 + 3760 + 00)^3 \\
 &:= (5 + 3 - 15 + 7 + 3760 + 00)^3 \\
 \mathbf{53242246728} &:= (-532 + 4224 + 6 + 72 - 8)^3 \\
 \mathbf{53369722125} &:= (53 + 3697 + 22 - 12 + 5)^3 \\
 &:= (-53 + 3697 - 2 - 2 + 125)^3 \\
 \mathbf{53527912321} &:= (535 - 2 - 7 - 9 - 1 - 2 - 32 - 1)^4 \\
 &:= (535 - 27 - 9 - 12 - 3 - 2 - 1)^4 \\
 &:= (535 - 27 + 9 - 1 - 2 - 32 - 1)^4 \\
 &:= (535 + 2 - 79 - 1 + 23 + 2 - 1)^4 \\
 &:= (535 + 2 - 79 + 1 + 23 - 2 + 1)^4 \\
 &:= (535 - 2 - 79 + 1 + 23 + 2 + 1)^4 \\
 &:= (535 + 2 - 79 + 1 - 2 + 3 + 21)^4 \\
 &:= (535 - 2 - 79 + 1 + 2 + 3 + 21)^4 \\
 &:= (535 - 2 - 7 - 9 - 12 - 3 - 21)^4 \\
 &:= (53 + 527 - 91 - 2 - 3 - 2 - 1)^4 \\
 &:= (-53 + 527 - 9 + 12 + 3 + 2 - 1)^4 \\
 &:= (53 + 5 + 2 + 7 + 91 + 2 + 321)^4 \\
 &:= (5 + 352 + 7 + 91 + 23 + 2 + 1)^4 \\
 &:= (5 + 352 + 7 + 91 + 2 + 3 + 21)^4 \\
 &:= (5 + 352 - 7 + 9 + 123 - 2 + 1)^4 \\
 &:= (5 + 352 + 7 - 9 + 123 + 2 + 1)^4 \\
 &:= (5 + 3 + 527 - 9 - 12 - 32 - 1)^4 \\
 &:= (5 + 3 + 527 - 9 - 1 - 23 - 21)^4
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 &:= (5 + 3 + 52 + 7 + 91 + 2 + 321)^4 \\
 &:= (5 - 3 + 5 + 2 + 791 + 2 - 321)^4 \\
 &:= (535 - 27 + 9 - 12 - 3 - 21)^4 \\
 &:= (5 + 352 + 79 + 12 + 32 + 1)^4 \\
 &:= (5 + 352 + 79 + 1 + 23 + 21)^4 \\
 &:= (5 - 35 + 279 + 1 + 232 - 1)^4 \\
 &:= (5 - 35 + 279 - 1 + 232 + 1)^4 \\
 &:= (5 + 35 + 27 + 91 + 2 + 321)^4 \\
 &:= (53 + 5 + 279 + 123 + 21)^4 \\
 &:= (535 + 279 - 12 - 321)^4 \\
 \mathbf{53667955648} &:= (5 + 3667 + 95 - 5 + 6 - 4 + 8)^3 \\
 &:= (-5 + 3667 + 95 + 5 + 6 - 4 + 8)^3 \\
 &:= (5 + 3667 - 9 + 55 + 6 + 48)^3 \\
 &:= (5 + 3667 - 9 + 5 + 56 + 48)^3 \\
 \mathbf{53710650917} &:= (-5 + 3710 + 65 + 09 + 1 - 7)^3 \\
 \mathbf{53753368824} &:= (-5 + 3753 + 36 - 8 - 8 + 2 + 4)^3 \\
 &:= (5 + 3 + 75 - 3 + 3688 + 2 + 4)^3 \\
 &:= (5 - 3 + 75 + 3 + 3688 + 2 + 4)^3 \\
 &:= (53 + 7 + 5 - 3 + 3688 + 24)^3 \\
 &:= (5 - 3 + 7 + 53 + 3688 + 24)^3 \\
 \mathbf{53796109375} &:= (-5 + 3796 - 10 + 9 - 3 - 7 - 5)^3 \\
 \mathbf{53838872576} &:= (5 + 3838 - 87 + 2 + 5 + 7 + 6)^3 \\
 \mathbf{53838872576} &:= (-5 + 3 - 8 + 3887 - 25 - 76)^3 \\
 \mathbf{53974440976} &:= (5 + 3 + 9 + 7 - 4 + 440 + 9 + 7 + 6)^4 \\
 &:= (539 - 7 - 44 + 4 - 09 - 7 + 6)^4 \\
 &:= (539 - 7 + 4 - 44 - 09 - 7 + 6)^4 \\
 &:= (539 - 7 + 4 - 4 - 40 - 9 - 7 + 6)^4 \\
 &:= (539 - 7 - 4 + 4 - 40 - 9 - 7 + 6)^4 \\
 &:= (5 + 397 + 44 + 40 + 9 - 7 - 6)^4 \\
 &:= (5 + 3 + 97 + 444 + 09 - 76)^4 \\
 &:= (5 + 3 + 97 + 4 + 440 + 9 - 76)^4 \\
 &:= (-5 + 39 + 7 - 44 + 409 + 76)^4 \\
 &:= (5 + 3 + 97 + 44 + 409 - 76)^4 \\
 \mathbf{54002323456} &:= (5 + 40 + 0232345 - 6)^2 \\
 \mathbf{54138849687} &:= (5 + 4 + 1 + 3884 - 96 - 8 - 7)^3 \\
 \mathbf{54353799872} &:= (5 + 43 + 5 + 3799 + 8 - 72)^3 \\
 \mathbf{54423757521} &:= (544 + 2 + 3 - 75 + 7 + 5 - 2 - 1)^4 \\
 &:= (544 - 2 + 3 - 75 + 7 + 5 + 2 - 1)^4
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 & := (544 + 2 - 3 - 75 + 7 + 5 + 2 + 1)^4 & := (544 + 23 + 7 + 5 - 75 - 21)^4 \\
 & := (544 - 2 + 3 - 7 - 57 + 5 - 2 - 1)^4 & := (54 + 4 - 2 - 37 - 57 + 521)^4 \\
 & := (544 - 2 - 3 + 7 - 57 - 5 - 2 + 1)^4 & := (5 + 442 - 37 + 57 - 5 + 21)^4 \\
 & := (544 + 2 - 3 - 7 - 57 + 5 - 2 + 1)^4 & := (-5 + 442 - 37 + 57 + 5 + 21)^4 \\
 & := (544 + 2 + 3 - 7 - 57 - 5 + 2 + 1)^4 & := (5 + 44 - 23 - 7 - 57 + 521)^4 \\
 & := (544 - 2 - 3 - 7 - 57 + 5 + 2 + 1)^4 & := (54 - 42 + 375 + 75 + 21)^4 \\
 & := (544 + 2 + 3 + 7 + 5 - 75 - 2 - 1)^4 & \mathbf{54439939000} := (-54 + 43 - 99 + 3900 + 0)^3 \\
 & := (544 - 2 + 3 + 7 + 5 - 75 + 2 - 1)^4 & \mathbf{54569318257} := (54 + 569 + 3182 - 5 - 7)^3 \\
 & := (544 + 2 - 3 + 7 + 5 - 75 + 2 + 1)^4 & \mathbf{54612490184} := (-5 + 4612 + 4 - 901 + 84)^3 \\
 & := (544 - 2 + 3 - 7 + 5 - 7 - 52 - 1)^4 & \mathbf{54622233796} := (-54 - 6 - 22 + 233796)^2 \\
 & := (544 - 2 - 3 + 7 - 5 - 7 - 52 + 1)^4 & \mathbf{54655684875} := (5 + 4655 + 6 + 8 - 4 - 875)^3 \\
 & := (544 + 2 - 3 - 7 + 5 - 7 - 52 + 1)^4 & \mathbf{54742142573} := (5 - 47 - 421 + 4257 + 3)^3 \\
 & := (544 - 2 - 3 - 7 - 5 + 7 - 52 + 1)^4 & \mathbf{54823412736} := (5 + 48 + 234127 - 36)^2 \\
 & := (-54 - 4 - 2 + 3 + 7 + 5 + 7 + 521)^4 & \mathbf{54875873536} := (54 - 8 + 7 - 5 - 8 - 7 + 3 - 5 - 3 - 6)^8 \\
 & := (5 + 4 + 4 - 2 - 37 - 5 - 7 + 521)^4 & := (54 - 8 - 7 - 5 - 8 + 7 + 3 - 5 - 3 - 6)^8 \\
 & := (-5 + 4 + 4 - 2 - 37 + 5 - 7 + 521)^4 & := (54 - 8 - 7 + 5 - 8 - 7 - 3 + 5 - 3 - 6)^8 \\
 & := (-5 + 4 - 4 + 2 - 37 - 5 + 7 + 521)^4 & := (54 - 8 + 7 - 5 - 8 - 7 - 3 - 5 + 3 - 6)^8 \\
 & := (-5 - 4 + 4 + 2 - 37 - 5 + 7 + 521)^4 & := (54 - 8 - 7 - 5 - 8 + 7 - 3 - 5 + 3 - 6)^8 \\
 & := (5 + 4 + 4 + 2 - 3 + 7 - 57 + 521)^4 & := (-5 - 4 - 8 - 7 + 58 - 7 + 3 - 5 + 3 - 6)^8 \\
 & := (544 + 23 - 75 - 7 - 5 + 2 + 1)^4 & := (-5 - 4 - 8 - 7 - 5 - 8 + 73 - 5 - 3 - 6)^8 \\
 & := (544 + 23 - 7 - 5 - 75 + 2 + 1)^4 & := (5 - 4 + 8 + 7 - 5 - 8 - 7 + 35 - 3 - 6)^8 \\
 & := (544 + 2 + 3 - 75 - 7 - 5 + 21)^4 & := (-5 - 4 + 8 + 7 + 5 - 8 - 7 + 35 - 3 - 6)^8 \\
 & := (544 - 2 - 3 - 75 - 7 + 5 + 21)^4 & := (-5 + 4 + 8 - 7 - 5 + 8 - 7 + 35 - 3 - 6)^8 \\
 & := (544 + 2 + 3 + 7 - 57 + 5 - 21)^4 & := (5 - 4 - 8 + 7 - 5 + 8 - 7 + 35 - 3 - 6)^8 \\
 & := (544 + 2 + 3 - 7 - 5 - 75 + 21)^4 & := (-5 - 4 - 8 + 7 + 5 + 8 - 7 + 35 - 3 - 6)^8 \\
 & := (544 - 2 - 3 - 7 + 5 - 75 + 21)^4 & := (5 - 4 + 8 - 7 - 5 - 8 + 7 + 35 - 3 - 6)^8 \\
 & := (54 - 4 - 2 + 375 + 7 + 52 + 1)^4 & := (-5 - 4 + 8 - 7 + 5 - 8 + 7 + 35 - 3 - 6)^8 \\
 & := (-54 + 4 - 2 - 37 + 575 - 2 - 1)^4 & := (5 - 4 - 8 - 7 - 5 + 8 + 7 + 35 - 3 - 6)^8 \\
 & := (-54 - 4 + 2 - 37 + 575 + 2 - 1)^4 & := (-5 - 4 - 8 - 7 + 5 + 8 + 7 + 35 - 3 - 6)^8 \\
 & := (5 + 442 - 37 - 5 + 75 + 2 + 1)^4 & := (5 + 4 + 8 - 7 - 5 - 8 - 7 + 35 + 3 - 6)^8 \\
 & := (-5 + 442 - 37 + 5 + 75 + 2 + 1)^4 & := (-5 + 4 + 8 - 7 + 5 - 8 - 7 + 35 + 3 - 6)^8 \\
 & := (5 + 44 - 2 - 3 - 75 - 7 + 521)^4 & := (5 - 4 - 8 + 7 + 5 - 8 - 7 + 35 + 3 - 6)^8 \\
 & := (-5 + 44 + 2 + 3 - 75 - 7 + 521)^4 & := (5 + 4 - 8 - 7 - 5 + 8 - 7 + 35 + 3 - 6)^8 \\
 & := (-5 + 4 + 42 + 3 - 75 - 7 + 521)^4 & := (-5 + 4 - 8 - 7 + 5 + 8 - 7 + 35 + 3 - 6)^8 \\
 & := (-5 - 4 + 42 - 3 - 75 + 7 + 521)^4 & := (5 - 4 - 8 - 7 + 5 - 8 + 7 + 35 + 3 - 6)^8 \\
 & := (-5 + 4 + 4 + 23 - 7 - 57 + 521)^4 & := (5 + 4 - 8 - 7 + 5 - 8 - 7 + 35 - 3 + 6)^8 \\
 & := (544 + 23 - 75 + 7 + 5 - 21)^4 & := (-5 - 4 - 8 + 7 - 5 - 8 + 7 + 35 - 3 + 6)^8 \\
 & := (544 - 23 - 7 - 57 + 5 + 21)^4 &
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} & := (-5+4-8+7-5-8-7+35+3+6)^8 & := (-5-48+75+8-7-3+5+3-6)^8 \\ & := (-5+4-8-7-5-8+7+35+3+6)^8 & := (5-48+75-8-7+3+5+3-6)^8 \\ & := (-5+4-8+7-5-8-7-3+53-6)^8 & := (-5-48+75-8+7+3-5-3+6)^8 \\ & := (-5+4-8-7-5-8+7-3+53-6)^8 & := (5-48+75-8-7-3+5-3+6)^8 \\ & := (-5-4+8-7-5-8-7+3+53-6)^8 & := (-5-48+75-8+7-3-5+3+6)^8 \\ & := (-5-4-8-7-5+8-7+3+53-6)^8 & := (5-48+7+58+7-3+5-3-6)^8 \\ & := (5-4-8-7-5-8-7-3+53+6)^8 & := (5-48+7+58-7+3-5+3+6)^8 \\ & := (-5-4-8-7+5-8-7-3+53+6)^8 & := (5-48-7+58+7+3-5+3+6)^8 \\ & := (-5+4+8+7-5-8-7-3-5+36)^8 & := (-5-48+7+58-7+3+5+3+6)^8 \\ & := (-5+4-8+7-5+8-7-3-5+36)^8 & := (-5-48-7+58+7+3+5+3+6)^8 \\ & := (-5+4+8-7-5-8+7-3-5+36)^8 & := (5-48-7+5+8+73-5-3-6)^8 \\ & := (5-4-8+7-5-8+7-3-5+36)^8 & := (5-48-7-5+8+73+5-3-6)^8 \\ & := (-5-4-8+7+5-8+7-3-5+36)^8 & := (-5-48-7+5+8+73+5-3-6)^8 \\ & := (-5+4-8-7-5+8+7-3-5+36)^8 & := (-5-48+7-5+8+73-5+3-6)^8 \\ & := (5+4-8+7-5-8-7+3-5+36)^8 & := (5-48-7+5-8+73+5+3-6)^8 \\ & := (-5+4-8+7+5-8-7+3-5+36)^8 & := (5-48+7-5-8+73-5-3+6)^8 \\ & := (-5-4+8-7-5+8-7+3-5+36)^8 & := (-5-48+7+5-8+73-5-3+6)^8 \\ & := (5+4-8-7-5-8+7+3-5+36)^8 & := (-5-48+7-5-8+73+5-3+6)^8 \\ & := (-5+4-8-7+5-8+7+3-5+36)^8 & := (5+48+7+5+8-7-35-3-6)^8 \\ & := (5+4-8-7+5-8-7-3+5+36)^8 & := (5+48-7+5+8+7-35-3-6)^8 \\ & := (-5-4-8+7-5-8+7-3+5+36)^8 & := (-5+48+7-5+8+7-35+3-6)^8 \\ & := (-5+4-8+7-5-8-7+3+5+36)^8 & := (5+48+7-5-8+7-35-3+6)^8 \\ & := (-5+4-8-7-5-8+7+3+5+36)^8 & := (-5+48+7+5-8+7-35-3+6)^8 \\ & := (-54+87+5+8-7-3-5-3-6)^8 & := (5-48+7+5+8+7+35-3+6)^8 \\ & := (-54+87-5+8-7-3+5-3-6)^8 & := (5+48+7+5+8-7+3-53+6)^8 \\ & := (-54+87+5-8-7+3+5-3-6)^8 & := (5+48-7+5+8+7+3-53+6)^8 \\ & := (-54+87-5-8+7+3-5+3-6)^8 & := (5-48+7-5+8-7+3+53+6)^8 \\ & := (-54+87+5-8-7-3+5+3-6)^8 & := (-5-48+7+5+8-7+3+53+6)^8 \\ & := (-54+87-5-8+7-3-5-3+6)^8 & := (5-48-7-5+8+7+3+53+6)^8 \\ & := (-54+8-7+5+87-3-5-3-6)^8 & := (-5-48-7+5+8+7+3+53+6)^8 \\ & := (-54+8-7-5+87-3+5-3-6)^8 & := (5+48+7+5+8-7-3-5-36)^8 \\ & := (-54-8-7+5+87+3+5-3-6)^8 & := (5+48-7+5+8+7-3-5-36)^8 \\ & := (-54-8+7-5+87+3-5+3-6)^8 & := (-5+48+7-5+8+7+3-5-36)^8 \\ & := (-54-8-7+5+87-3+5+3-6)^8 & := (5+48+7-5+8-7-3+5-36)^8 \\ & := (-54-8+7-5+87-3-5-3+6)^8 & := (-5+48+7+5+8-7-3+5-36)^8 \\ & := (5-48+75+8-7+3-5-3-6)^8 & := (5+48-7-5+8+7-3+5-36)^8 \\ & := (-5-48+75+8-7+3+5-3-6)^8 & := (-5+48-7+5+8+7-3+5-36)^8 \\ & := (5-48+75+8-7-3-5+3-6)^8 & := (5+48+7+5-8-7+3+5-36)^8 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} &:= (5 + 48 - 7 + 5 - 8 + 7 + 3 + 5 - 36)^8 & &:= (548 + 7 + 5 - 87 - 3 + 5 + 3 + 6)^4 \\ &:= (5 - 48 + 7 + 5 + 8 + 7 - 3 + 5 + 36)^8 & &:= (54 - 8 - 75 - 8 + 73 - 5 - 3 - 6)^8 \\ &:= (5 - 4 + 87 - 58 - 7 + 3 + 5 - 3 - 6)^8 & &:= (54 + 8 - 75 - 8 - 7 + 3 + 53 - 6)^8 \\ &:= (-5 - 4 + 87 - 58 + 7 + 3 - 5 + 3 - 6)^8 & &:= (54 - 8 - 75 + 8 - 7 + 3 + 53 - 6)^8 \\ &:= (5 - 4 + 87 - 58 - 7 - 3 + 5 + 3 - 6)^8 & &:= (54 + 8 - 75 + 8 - 7 + 3 - 5 + 36)^8 \\ &:= (-5 - 4 + 87 - 58 + 7 - 3 - 5 - 3 + 6)^8 & &:= (54 - 8 - 7 + 58 - 73 - 5 - 3 + 6)^8 \\ &:= (-5 + 4 + 87 - 58 - 7 + 3 - 5 - 3 + 6)^8 & &:= (-54 - 8 + 7 + 58 - 7 + 35 - 3 - 6)^8 \\ &:= (-5 + 4 + 87 - 58 - 7 - 3 - 5 + 3 + 6)^8 & &:= (-54 - 8 - 7 + 58 + 7 + 35 - 3 - 6)^8 \\ &:= (5 + 4 + 87 + 5 + 8 - 73 - 5 - 3 - 6)^8 & &:= (54 + 8 - 7 - 58 - 7 + 35 + 3 - 6)^8 \\ &:= (5 + 4 + 87 - 5 + 8 - 73 + 5 - 3 - 6)^8 & &:= (54 - 8 + 7 - 58 - 7 + 3 - 5 + 36)^8 \\ &:= (-5 + 4 + 87 + 5 + 8 - 73 + 5 - 3 - 6)^8 & &:= (54 - 8 - 7 - 58 + 7 + 3 - 5 + 36)^8 \\ &:= (5 + 4 + 87 + 5 - 8 - 73 + 5 + 3 - 6)^8 & &:= (54 - 8 - 7 + 5 - 8 - 73 + 53 + 6)^8 \\ &:= (5 - 4 + 87 - 5 + 8 - 73 - 5 + 3 + 6)^8 & &:= (-54 - 8 - 7 - 5 - 8 + 73 - 5 + 36)^8 \\ &:= (-5 - 4 + 87 + 5 + 8 - 73 - 5 + 3 + 6)^8 & &:= (-54 + 8 + 7 + 5 - 8 - 7 + 35 + 36)^8 \\ &:= (-5 - 4 + 87 - 5 + 8 - 73 + 5 + 3 + 6)^8 & &:= (-54 - 8 + 7 + 5 + 8 - 7 + 35 + 36)^8 \\ &:= (5 + 4 - 87 + 5 + 8 + 73 + 5 + 3 + 6)^8 & &:= (-54 + 8 - 7 + 5 - 8 + 7 + 35 + 36)^8 \\ &:= (-5 + 4 + 87 - 5 - 8 - 7 - 35 - 3 - 6)^8 & &:= (-54 - 8 - 7 + 5 + 8 + 7 + 35 + 36)^8 \\ &:= (5 - 4 + 87 - 5 + 8 - 7 - 3 - 53 - 6)^8 & &:= (-54 + 8 + 7 + 5 - 8 - 7 - 3 + 536)^4 \\ &:= (-5 - 4 + 87 + 5 + 8 - 7 - 3 - 53 - 6)^8 & &:= (-54 - 8 + 7 + 5 + 8 - 7 - 3 + 536)^4 \\ &:= (5 - 4 + 87 + 5 - 8 - 7 + 3 - 53 - 6)^8 & &:= (-54 + 8 - 7 + 5 - 8 + 7 - 3 + 536)^4 \\ &:= (-5 - 4 + 87 - 5 - 8 + 7 - 3 - 53 + 6)^8 & &:= (-54 - 8 - 7 + 5 + 8 + 7 - 3 + 536)^4 \\ &:= (-5 + 4 + 87 - 5 - 8 - 7 + 3 - 53 + 6)^8 & &:= (5 + 487 + 5 + 8 + 7 + 3 + 5 - 36)^4 \\ &:= (-5 + 4 + 87 - 5 - 8 - 7 - 3 - 5 - 36)^8 & &:= (5 + 48 + 7 + 5 - 87 + 35 + 3 + 6)^8 \\ &:= (5 + 4 + 8 - 75 + 87 - 3 + 5 - 3 - 6)^8 & &:= (5 + 48 + 7 + 5 - 87 - 3 + 53 - 6)^8 \\ &:= (5 - 4 + 8 - 75 + 87 + 3 - 5 - 3 + 6)^8 & &:= (5 - 48 + 7 + 5 + 87 - 3 + 5 - 36)^8 \\ &:= (-5 - 4 + 8 - 75 + 87 + 3 + 5 - 3 + 6)^8 & &:= (5 + 48 + 7 + 5 - 87 + 3 + 5 + 36)^8 \\ &:= (5 - 4 + 8 - 75 + 87 - 3 - 5 + 3 + 6)^8 & &:= (5 - 4 - 87 + 587 - 3 - 5 - 3 - 6)^4 \\ &:= (-5 - 4 + 8 - 75 + 87 - 3 + 5 + 3 + 6)^8 & &:= (-5 - 4 - 87 + 587 - 3 + 5 - 3 - 6)^4 \\ &:= (5 + 4 + 8 + 75 - 87 + 3 + 5 + 3 + 6)^8 & &:= (5 - 4 + 87 - 5 - 87 + 35 - 3 - 6)^8 \\ &:= (5 - 4 - 8 - 75 + 87 + 3 + 5 + 3 + 6)^8 & &:= (-5 - 4 + 87 + 5 - 87 + 35 - 3 - 6)^8 \\ &:= (-5 + 4 - 8 - 7 - 5 + 87 - 35 - 3 - 6)^8 & &:= (5 - 4 - 87 - 5 + 87 + 35 - 3 - 6)^8 \\ &:= (5 - 4 + 8 - 7 - 5 + 87 - 3 - 53 - 6)^8 & &:= (-5 - 4 - 87 + 5 + 87 + 35 - 3 - 6)^8 \\ &:= (-5 - 4 + 8 - 7 + 5 + 87 - 3 - 53 - 6)^8 & &:= (-5 + 4 + 87 - 5 - 87 - 3 - 5 + 36)^8 \\ &:= (5 - 4 - 8 - 7 + 5 + 87 + 3 - 53 - 6)^8 & &:= (-5 + 4 - 87 - 5 + 87 - 3 - 5 + 36)^8 \\ &:= (-5 - 4 - 8 + 7 - 5 + 87 - 3 - 53 + 6)^8 & &:= (5 + 4 - 8 - 75 - 8 + 73 - 5 + 36)^8 \\ &:= (-5 + 4 - 8 - 7 - 5 + 87 + 3 - 53 + 6)^8 & &:= (-5 + 4 - 8 - 75 - 8 + 73 + 5 + 36)^8 \\ &:= (-5 + 4 - 8 - 7 - 5 + 87 - 3 - 5 - 36)^8 & &:= (5 + 4 + 8 + 75 + 8 - 7 - 35 - 36)^8 \\ &:= (548 + 7 + 5 - 87 + 3 + 5 - 3 + 6)^4 & &:= (-5 - 4 - 8 + 7 + 58 - 73 + 53 - 6)^8 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 & := (-5 - 4 + 8 + 7 + 58 - 73 - 5 + 36)^8 \\
 & := (-5 - 4 - 8 - 7 - 58 + 73 - 5 + 36)^8 \\
 & := (5 - 4 + 8 + 7 - 58 - 7 + 35 + 36)^8 \\
 & := (5 - 4 + 8 - 7 - 58 + 7 + 35 + 36)^8 \\
 & := (5 - 4 + 8 + 7 - 58 - 7 - 3 + 536)^4 \\
 & := (5 - 4 + 8 - 7 - 58 + 7 - 3 + 536)^4 \\
 & := (5 + 4 + 8 - 7 - 58 - 7 + 3 + 536)^4 \\
 & := (5 + 4 + 8 + 7 + 5 - 8 - 73 + 536)^4 \\
 & := (5 + 4 - 8 + 7 + 5 + 8 - 73 + 536)^4 \\
 & := (548 - 75 - 8 - 7 + 35 - 3 - 6)^4 \\
 & := (548 + 7 + 5 + 8 - 7 - 3 - 536)^8 \\
 & := (548 - 7 + 5 + 8 + 7 - 3 - 536)^8 \\
 & := (-54 + 87 + 58 - 73 - 5 + 3 + 6)^8 \\
 & := (-54 + 87 + 58 - 7 - 3 - 53 - 6)^8 \\
 & := (54 + 87 + 5 + 8 - 73 - 53 - 6)^8 \\
 & := (-54 + 87 - 5 + 8 - 73 + 53 + 6)^8 \\
 & := (54 - 87 + 5 + 8 + 73 + 5 - 36)^8 \\
 & := (54 + 87 - 5 + 8 - 7 + 353 - 6)^4 \\
 & := (-54 + 87 + 5 - 8 - 7 + 35 - 36)^8 \\
 & := (-54 + 8 - 75 + 87 - 3 + 53 + 6)^8 \\
 & := (54 + 8 + 75 - 87 + 3 + 5 - 36)^8 \\
 & := (-54 + 8 - 7 + 587 - 3 - 53 + 6)^4 \\
 & := (-54 - 8 - 7 + 587 - 3 + 5 - 36)^4 \\
 & := (54 + 8 - 7 - 5 + 87 + 353 - 6)^4 \\
 & := (-54 - 8 - 7 + 5 + 87 + 35 - 36)^8 \\
 & := (5 - 48 - 75 + 8 + 73 + 53 + 6)^8 \\
 & := (5 + 48 + 75 + 8 - 73 - 5 - 36)^8 \\
 & := (-5 + 48 + 75 + 8 - 73 + 5 - 36)^8 \\
 & := (-5 - 48 + 75 + 8 - 7 + 35 - 36)^8 \\
 & := (-5 - 48 + 75 - 8 + 7 - 35 + 36)^8 \\
 & := (5 - 48 - 7 + 58 + 73 - 53 - 6)^8 \\
 & := (5 + 48 + 7 + 58 + 7 + 353 + 6)^4 \\
 & := (5 + 4 + 87 + 58 - 73 - 53 - 6)^8 \\
 & := (-5 - 4 + 87 + 58 - 73 - 5 - 36)^8 \\
 & := (5 + 4 - 87 + 58 + 73 + 5 - 36)^8 \\
 & := (-5 + 4 + 87 + 58 - 7 + 353 - 6)^4 \\
 & := (5 - 4 + 87 - 58 - 7 + 35 - 36)^8 \\
 & := (-5 + 4 + 87 - 58 - 7 - 35 + 36)^8 \\
 & := (5 - 4 + 8 - 75 + 87 - 35 + 36)^8 \\
 & := (-54 - 87 + 587 + 35 - 3 + 6)^4 \\
 & := (-54 - 87 + 587 - 3 + 5 + 36)^4 \\
 & := (-54 + 87 + 5 + 87 + 353 + 6)^4 \\
 & := (-54 + 87 + 5 - 87 + 35 + 36)^8 \\
 & := (-54 - 87 + 5 + 87 + 35 + 36)^8 \\
 & := (-54 + 87 + 5 - 87 - 3 + 536)^4 \\
 & := (-54 - 87 + 5 + 87 - 3 + 536)^4 \\
 & := (-54 + 8 + 75 - 8 - 73 + 536)^4 \\
 & := (-54 - 8 + 75 + 8 - 73 + 536)^4 \\
 & := (-5 + 487 - 5 + 8 + 73 - 536)^8 \\
 & := (5 - 48 + 75 - 87 + 3 + 536)^4 \\
 & := (5 - 4 + 8 - 758 + 735 + 36)^8 \\
 & := (548 + 75 + 8 - 73 - 536)^8 \\
 & := (-54 + 875 - 873 + 536)^4 \\
 & \mathbf{54930234384} := (5 + 4 + 9 - 30 + 234384)^2 \\
 & \mathbf{55132330616} := (551 + 3233 + 06 + 16)^3 \\
 & \quad := (5 + 513 - 2 + 3306 - 16)^3 \\
 & \mathbf{55330800625} := (553 + 3 - 080 + 06 - 2 + 5)^4 \\
 & \quad := (553 - 3 - 08 - 0062 + 5)^4 \\
 & \mathbf{55655459432} := (-5565 - 54 + 5 + 9432)^3 \\
 & \mathbf{55730836701} := (55 + 73 + 08 + 3 - 6 + 7 + 01)^5 \\
 & \quad := (55 + 7 + 3 + 08 + 3 - 6 + 70 + 1)^5 \\
 & \quad := (55 + 7 - 3 + 08 - 3 + 6 + 70 + 1)^5 \\
 & \quad := (-5 + 57 + 3 + 08 + 3 + 6 + 70 - 1)^5 \\
 & \quad := (5 + 57 + 3 + 08 + 3 - 6 + 70 + 1)^5 \\
 & \quad := (5 + 57 - 3 + 08 - 3 + 6 + 70 + 1)^5 \\
 & \quad := (5 - 5 + 73 + 08 - 3 - 6 + 70 - 1)^5 \\
 & \quad := (-5 + 5 + 73 + 08 - 3 - 6 + 70 - 1)^5 \\
 & \quad := (5 + 5 + 73 - 08 + 3 - 6 + 70 - 1)^5 \\
 & \quad := (5 - 5 - 7 - 3 + 083 + 67 + 01)^5 \\
 & \quad := (-5 + 5 - 7 - 3 + 083 + 67 + 01)^5 \\
 & \quad := (55 - 7 + 30 - 8 + 3 + 67 + 01)^5 \\
 & \quad := (5 + 5 - 7 + 3 + 0836 - 701)^5 \\
 & \quad := (-55 - 7 + 308 - 36 - 70 + 1)^5 \\
 & \quad := (-5 - 57 + 308 - 36 - 70 + 1)^5 \\
 & \mathbf{55788550416} := (557 + 8 - 85 + 5 - 04 - 1 + 6)^4 \\
 & \quad := (557 + 8 - 85 - 5 + 04 + 1 + 6)^4
 \end{aligned}$$

$:= (-5 + 578 - 85 - 5 - 04 + 1 + 6)^4$	$:= (-5 - 6 - 2 + 491 + 3 - 4 + 5 + 6 - 1)^4$
$:= (5 + 5 + 78 - 8 - 5 - 5 + 0416)^4$	$:= (5 + 6 + 2 + 491 - 3 - 4 - 5 - 6 + 1)^4$
$:= (5 - 5 + 78 - 8 + 5 - 5 + 0416)^4$	$:= (-5 + 6 - 2 + 491 + 3 + 4 - 5 - 6 + 1)^4$
$:= (-5 + 5 + 78 - 8 + 5 - 5 + 0416)^4$	$:= (-5 + 6 + 2 + 491 - 3 - 4 + 5 - 6 + 1)^4$
$:= (5 - 5 + 78 - 8 - 5 + 5 + 0416)^4$	$:= (5 - 6 - 2 + 491 + 3 - 4 + 5 - 6 + 1)^4$
$:= (-5 + 5 + 78 - 8 - 5 + 5 + 0416)^4$	$:= (5 - 6 + 2 + 491 - 3 - 4 - 5 + 6 + 1)^4$
$:= (-5 - 5 + 78 - 8 + 5 + 5 + 0416)^4$	$:= (-5 - 6 - 2 + 491 + 3 + 4 - 5 + 6 + 1)^4$
$:= (-5 - 5 - 7 + 8 - 8 + 550 - 41 - 6)^4$	$:= (-5 - 6 + 2 + 491 - 3 - 4 + 5 + 6 + 1)^4$
$:= (-5 - 5 - 7 - 8 + 8 + 550 - 41 - 6)^4$	$:= (5 + 6 + 2 + 4 + 9 + 1 + 3 + 456 + 1)^4$
$:= (5 + 5 - 7 + 8 - 8 - 5 + 504 - 16)^4$	$:= (562 - 4 - 9 + 1 - 3 - 4 + 5 - 61)^4$
$:= (5 + 5 - 7 - 8 + 8 - 5 + 504 - 16)^4$	$:= (-5 - 62 + 4 - 9 - 1 + 3 - 4 + 561)^4$
$:= (5 - 5 - 7 + 8 - 8 + 5 + 504 - 16)^4$	$:= (-5 - 62 - 4 - 9 - 1 + 3 + 4 + 561)^4$
$:= (-5 + 5 - 7 + 8 - 8 + 5 + 504 - 16)^4$	$:= (-5 + 6 + 24 + 9 + 1 - 3 + 456 - 1)^4$
$:= (5 - 5 - 7 - 8 + 8 + 5 + 504 - 16)^4$	$:= (-5 + 6 + 24 + 9 - 1 - 3 + 456 + 1)^4$
$:= (-5 + 5 - 7 - 8 + 8 + 5 + 504 - 16)^4$	$:= (5 - 6 + 24 + 9 + 1 - 3 + 456 + 1)^4$
$:= (-5 + 57 + 8 - 85 + 504 + 1 + 6)^4$	$:= (5 + 6 + 24 - 9 + 1 + 3 + 456 + 1)^4$
$:= (5 - 57 + 8 - 8 + 550 + 4 - 16)^4$	$:= (-5 - 6 - 2 + 49 - 1 - 3 + 456 - 1)^4$
$:= (5 - 57 - 8 + 8 + 550 + 4 - 16)^4$	$:= (562 + 4 + 9 + 1 - 34 - 56 + 1)^4$
$:= (5 + 5 - 78 - 8 + 550 - 4 + 16)^4$	$:= (56 - 2 + 491 + 3 - 4 - 56 - 1)^4$
$:= (55 + 78 - 8 - 55 + 0416)^4$	$:= (-56 - 2 + 491 + 3 - 4 + 56 - 1)^4$
$:= (-55 + 78 - 8 + 55 + 0416)^4$	$:= (56 + 2 + 491 - 3 - 4 - 56 + 1)^4$
$:= (55 + 78 - 8 - 5 - 50 + 416)^4$	$:= (-56 + 2 + 491 - 3 - 4 + 56 + 1)^4$
$:= (-55 + 78 - 8 + 5 + 50 + 416)^4$	$:= (56 - 2 + 4 + 91 + 345 - 6 - 1)^4$
55874402767 $:= (-55 - 8 - 74 + 4027 - 67)^3$	$:= (-56 - 2 - 4 + 91 + 3 + 456 - 1)^4$
$:= (-5 - 58 - 74 + 4027 - 67)^3$	$:= (-56 + 2 - 4 + 91 - 3 + 456 + 1)^4$
56137891789 $:= (-56 + 1 + 3789 - 1 + 7 + 89)^3$	$:= (56 + 2 - 4 - 9 - 13 + 456 - 1)^4$
$:= (-56 - 1 + 3789 + 1 + 7 + 89)^3$	$:= (-56 + 2 + 4 + 9 + 1 - 34 + 561)^4$
$:= (-5 + 61 + 3789 - 17 - 8 + 9)^3$	$:= (-5 + 624 - 91 - 3 - 45 + 6 + 1)^4$
$:= (-5 - 61 + 3789 + 17 + 89)^3$	$:= (5 - 62 + 491 + 3 + 45 + 6 - 1)^4$
56247237225 $:= (5 - 62 + 4 - 7 + 237225)^2$	$:= (-5 - 62 + 491 + 3 + 4 - 5 + 61)^4$
$:= (-5 - 6 - 2 - 47 + 237225)^2$	$:= (5 + 62 + 4 + 9 + 1 + 345 + 61)^4$
56249134561 $:= (5 + 6 - 2 + 491 + 3 - 4 - 5 - 6 - 1)^4$	$:= (5 + 6 - 2 + 491 + 3 + 45 - 61)^4$
$:= (5 - 6 + 2 + 491 + 3 + 4 - 5 - 6 - 1)^4$	$:= (-5 - 6 - 2 - 4 - 91 + 34 + 561)^4$
$:= (-5 + 6 - 2 + 491 + 3 - 4 + 5 - 6 - 1)^4$	$:= (562 + 49 - 134 + 5 + 6 - 1)^4$
$:= (5 - 6 - 2 + 491 - 3 + 4 + 5 - 6 - 1)^4$	$:= (-56 + 24 - 9 + 1 - 34 + 561)^4$
$:= (-5 - 6 + 2 + 491 + 3 + 4 + 5 - 6 - 1)^4$	$:= (-56 - 2 - 49 - 1 + 34 + 561)^4$
$:= (-5 + 6 + 2 + 491 - 3 - 4 - 5 + 6 - 1)^4$	56269946368 $:= (-5626 + 9 + 9463 - 6 - 8)^3$
$:= (5 - 6 - 2 + 491 + 3 - 4 - 5 + 6 - 1)^4$	56623104000 $:= (5 + 66 - 231 + 04000)^3$

$$\begin{aligned}
 \mathbf{56712564736} &:= (567 - 1 - 2 - 56 - 4 - 7 - 3 - 6)^4 \\
 &:= (567 + 1 + 2 - 5 + 6 - 4 - 73 - 6)^4 \\
 &:= (567 - 1 - 2 + 5 - 6 + 4 - 73 - 6)^4 \\
 &:= (567 + 1 + 2 - 5 - 6 - 4 - 73 + 6)^4 \\
 &:= (-56 - 7 + 1 + 2 + 564 - 7 - 3 - 6)^4 \\
 &:= (-56 - 7 - 1 - 2 + 564 - 7 + 3 - 6)^4 \\
 &:= (5 - 6 - 71 - 2 + 564 + 7 - 3 - 6)^4 \\
 &:= (-5 - 6 - 71 + 2 + 564 + 7 + 3 - 6)^4 \\
 &:= (-5 + 6 - 71 - 2 + 564 - 7 - 3 + 6)^4 \\
 &:= (-5 + 6 + 7 + 12 - 5 + 6 + 473 - 6)^4 \\
 &:= (-5 + 6 + 7 + 12 - 5 - 6 + 473 + 6)^4 \\
 &:= (-5 - 6 + 7 + 12 - 5 + 6 + 473 + 6)^4 \\
 &:= (5 - 6 + 7 - 1 - 2 + 564 - 73 - 6)^4 \\
 &:= (5 + 6 - 7 + 1 - 2 + 564 - 73 - 6)^4 \\
 &:= (-5 + 6 - 7 - 1 - 2 + 564 - 73 + 6)^4 \\
 &:= (5 - 6 - 7 + 1 - 2 + 564 - 73 + 6)^4 \\
 &:= (567 - 12 - 5 - 64 - 7 + 3 + 6)^4 \\
 &:= (567 - 12 - 5 - 6 - 47 - 3 - 6)^4 \\
 &:= (567 - 1 - 25 - 6 - 4 - 7 - 36)^4 \\
 &:= (567 + 1 + 2 - 5 + 6 - 47 - 36)^4 \\
 &:= (-5 - 67 + 12 + 564 - 7 - 3 - 6)^4 \\
 &:= (5 - 67 - 12 + 564 + 7 - 3 - 6)^4 \\
 &:= (-5 + 67 + 1 + 2 - 56 + 473 + 6)^4 \\
 &:= (567 - 12 - 56 - 47 + 36)^4
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 \mathbf{56800235584} &:= (5 + 68 - 002 + 3 + 5 - 5 - 8 - 4)^6 \\
 &:= (5 + 68 - 002 + 3 - 5 + 5 - 8 - 4)^6 \\
 &:= (-5 + 68 - 002 + 3 + 5 + 5 - 8 - 4)^6 \\
 &:= (5 + 68 - 002 - 3 - 5 - 5 + 8 - 4)^6 \\
 &:= (-5 + 68 + 002 + 3 - 5 - 5 + 8 - 4)^6 \\
 &:= (-5 + 68 - 002 - 3 + 5 - 5 + 8 - 4)^6 \\
 &:= (-5 + 68 - 002 - 3 - 5 + 5 + 8 - 4)^6 \\
 &:= (5 - 6 + 80 + 02 + 3 - 5 - 5 - 8 - 4)^6 \\
 &:= (5 - 6 + 80 - 02 - 3 + 5 - 5 - 8 - 4)^6 \\
 &:= (-5 - 6 + 80 + 02 + 3 + 5 - 5 - 8 - 4)^6 \\
 &:= (5 - 6 + 80 - 02 - 3 - 5 + 5 - 8 - 4)^6 \\
 &:= (-5 - 6 + 80 + 02 + 3 - 5 + 5 - 8 - 4)^6 \\
 &:= (-5 - 6 + 80 - 02 - 3 + 5 + 5 - 8 - 4)^6 \\
 &:= (-5 - 6 + 80 + 02 - 3 - 5 - 5 + 8 - 4)^6
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 &:= (-5 + 6 + 80 - 02 - 3 - 5 - 5 - 8 + 4)^6 \\
 &:= (-5 + 6 - 8 - 002 - 3 - 5 - 5 + 84)^6 \\
 &:= (5 + 68 - 0023 + 5 - 5 + 8 + 4)^6 \\
 &:= (5 + 68 - 0023 - 5 + 5 + 8 + 4)^6 \\
 &:= (-5 + 68 - 0023 + 5 + 5 + 8 + 4)^6 \\
 &:= (5 + 6 + 80 - 023 - 5 - 5 + 8 - 4)^6 \\
 &:= (-5 + 6 + 80 - 023 + 5 - 5 + 8 - 4)^6 \\
 &:= (-5 + 6 + 80 - 023 - 5 + 5 + 8 - 4)^6 \\
 &:= (5 - 6 + 80 - 023 + 5 + 5 - 8 + 4)^6 \\
 &:= (5 - 6 - 8 - 0023 + 5 + 5 + 84)^6 \\
 &:= (-56 + 80 + 02 + 35 + 5 - 8 + 4)^6 \\
 &:= (-56 + 80 - 02 - 3 + 55 - 8 - 4)^6 \\
 &:= (-56 - 8 + 002 + 35 + 5 + 84)^6 \\
 &:= (5 + 6 + 80 - 02 + 35 - 58 - 4)^6 \\
 &:= (5 - 6 + 80 + 02 + 35 - 58 + 4)^6 \\
 &:= (56 + 80 - 023 - 55 + 8 - 4)^6
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\mathbf{56888939736} := (56 - 88 - 89 + 3973 - 6)^3$$

$$\mathbf{56933326423} := (569 - 3 + 3326 - 42 - 3)^3$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 \mathbf{57178852641} &:= (-5 - 7 + 1 - 7 - 8 - 8 + 526 - 4 + 1)^4 \\
 &:= (571 - 78 - 8 + 5 - 2 + 6 - 4 - 1)^4 \\
 &:= (571 - 78 - 8 + 5 + 2 - 6 + 4 - 1)^4 \\
 &:= (571 - 78 + 8 - 5 + 2 - 6 - 4 + 1)^4 \\
 &:= (571 - 78 - 8 - 5 - 2 + 6 + 4 + 1)^4 \\
 &:= (5 + 7 + 1 + 7 - 8 - 8 + 526 - 41)^4 \\
 &:= (5 + 7 - 1 - 7 + 8 - 8 + 526 - 41)^4 \\
 &:= (5 - 7 - 1 + 7 + 8 - 8 + 526 - 41)^4 \\
 &:= (5 + 7 - 1 - 7 - 8 + 8 + 526 - 41)^4 \\
 &:= (5 - 7 - 1 + 7 - 8 + 8 + 526 - 41)^4 \\
 &:= (-57 + 17 + 8 - 8 + 526 + 4 - 1)^4 \\
 &:= (-57 + 17 - 8 + 8 + 526 + 4 - 1)^4 \\
 &:= (5 - 71 - 7 + 8 - 85 - 2 + 641)^4 \\
 &:= (5 + 7 + 1 - 78 - 85 - 2 + 641)^4 \\
 &:= (-5 + 7 + 1 + 7 - 88 + 526 + 41)^4 \\
 &:= (571 - 7 - 88 - 52 + 64 + 1)^4 \\
 &:= (5 - 71 + 78 - 8 + 526 - 41)^4 \\
 &:= (-57 - 178 + 85 - 2 + 641)^4
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\mathbf{57333846016} := (-5 - 7 + 3 + 3 + 3846 + 016)^3$$

$$:= (5 - 733 - 3 - 8 + 4601 - 6)^3$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 \mathbf{57378463793} &:= (57 + 3784 + 6 - 3 + 7 + 9 - 3)^3 & := (-5 - 7 + 73 + 53 + 3 - 9 + 2 + 32)^5 \\
 &:= (57 + 3784 - 6 + 3 + 7 + 9 + 3)^3 & := (-5 + 7 + 73 - 5 + 33 + 9 - 2 + 32)^5 \\
 &:= (-5 - 7 + 3784 + 6 + 3 + 79 - 3)^3 & := (5 - 7 + 73 - 5 + 33 + 9 + 2 + 32)^5 \\
 &:= (-5 - 7 + 3784 + 6 - 3 + 79 + 3)^3 & := (-5 - 7 + 73 + 5 + 33 + 9 + 2 + 32)^5 \\
 &:= (-57 - 3 + 78 + 46 + 3793)^3 & := (5 - 7 + 73 + 5 - 3 + 39 - 2 + 32)^5 \\
 \mathbf{57594240144} &:= (-57 - 5 - 94 + 240144)^2 & := (-5 + 7 + 73 - 5 + 3 + 39 - 2 + 32)^5 \\
 \mathbf{57601899928} &:= (5760 - 1899 - 9 + 2 + 8)^3 & := (5 - 7 + 73 - 5 + 3 + 39 + 2 + 32)^5 \\
 &:= (-57 - 6018 + 9 + 9928)^3 & := (-5 - 7 + 73 + 5 + 3 + 39 + 2 + 32)^5 \\
 \mathbf{57602400025} &:= (-5 + 7 + 6 + 0240002 - 5)^2 & := (5 - 7 + 73 + 5 + 3 + 3 + 92 - 32)^5 \\
 \mathbf{57648010000} &:= (576 + 4 - 80 - 10 + 000)^4 & := (-5 - 7 - 7 + 35 + 33 + 92 + 3 - 2)^5 \\
 \mathbf{57735339232} &:= (57 + 73 - 5 + 33 - 9 - 2 - 3 - 2)^5 & := (5 + 7 + 7 - 3 + 53 + 39 + 2 + 32)^5 \\
 &:= (57 + 7 + 35 + 33 + 9 + 2 - 3 + 2)^5 & := (57 + 73 - 5 + 33 + 9 - 23 - 2)^5 \\
 &:= (57 + 7 + 35 + 3 + 39 + 2 - 3 + 2)^5 & := (57 + 73 - 5 + 3 + 39 - 23 - 2)^5 \\
 &:= (57 + 7 + 35 - 3 + 39 + 2 + 3 + 2)^5 & := (57 - 7 + 35 - 3 + 39 + 23 - 2)^5 \\
 &:= (57 + 7 + 35 + 3 - 3 + 9 + 2 + 32)^5 & := (-57 - 7 - 35 + 3 - 3 + 9 + 232)^5 \\
 &:= (57 + 7 + 35 - 3 + 3 + 9 + 2 + 32)^5 & := (-57 - 7 - 35 - 3 + 3 + 9 + 232)^5 \\
 &:= (57 - 7 + 3 + 53 + 39 + 2 - 3 - 2)^5 & := (-57 + 7 - 3 + 5 - 33 - 9 + 232)^5 \\
 &:= (57 - 7 - 3 + 53 + 39 + 2 + 3 - 2)^5 & := (-57 - 7 + 3 - 5 - 33 + 9 + 232)^5 \\
 &:= (57 - 7 + 3 + 53 + 39 - 2 - 3 + 2)^5 & := (-57 + 7 - 3 + 5 - 3 - 39 + 232)^5 \\
 &:= (57 - 7 - 3 + 53 + 39 - 2 + 3 + 2)^5 & := (5 - 773 - 5 - 3 - 3 + 923 - 2)^5 \\
 &:= (57 - 7 + 3 + 53 - 3 + 9 - 2 + 32)^5 & := (-5 - 773 + 5 - 3 - 3 + 923 - 2)^5 \\
 &:= (57 - 7 - 3 + 53 + 3 + 9 - 2 + 32)^5 & := (-5 - 773 - 5 + 3 - 3 + 923 + 2)^5 \\
 &:= (57 + 7 + 3 + 53 - 3 - 9 + 2 + 32)^5 & := (-5 - 773 - 5 - 3 + 3 + 923 + 2)^5 \\
 &:= (57 + 7 - 3 + 53 + 3 - 9 + 2 + 32)^5 & := (-5 + 77 + 3 + 53 + 39 - 23 - 2)^5 \\
 &:= (57 + 7 - 3 + 5 + 33 + 9 + 2 + 32)^5 & := (-5 + 7 + 73 + 53 + 39 - 23 - 2)^5 \\
 &:= (57 + 7 + 3 + 5 - 3 + 39 + 2 + 32)^5 & := (5 - 7 + 73 + 53 + 39 - 23 + 2)^5 \\
 &:= (57 + 7 - 3 + 5 + 3 + 39 + 2 + 32)^5 & := (5 + 7 - 73 - 5 - 33 + 9 + 232)^5 \\
 &:= (-5 + 77 + 35 + 33 + 9 - 2 - 3 - 2)^5 & := (-5 + 7 - 73 + 5 - 33 + 9 + 232)^5 \\
 &:= (5 + 77 + 35 + 33 - 9 + 2 - 3 + 2)^5 & := (-5 + 7 + 7 + 353 + 3 + 9 - 232)^5 \\
 &:= (-5 + 77 + 35 + 3 + 39 - 2 - 3 - 2)^5 & := (-5 - 7 - 7 - 35 + 3 - 39 + 232)^5 \\
 &:= (-5 + 77 + 35 - 3 + 39 - 2 + 3 - 2)^5 & := (5 + 7 - 7 - 3 - 53 - 39 + 232)^5 \\
 &:= (5 + 77 + 35 + 3 - 3 - 9 + 2 + 32)^5 & := (5 - 7 + 7 - 3 - 53 - 39 + 232)^5 \\
 &:= (5 + 77 + 35 - 3 + 3 - 9 + 2 + 32)^5 & := (577 - 35 - 3 - 392 - 3 - 2)^5 \\
 &:= (5 + 77 - 3 + 5 - 33 + 92 - 3 + 2)^5 & := (577 - 3 - 5 - 3 - 392 - 32)^5 \\
 &:= (-5 + 77 + 3 - 5 + 33 + 9 - 2 + 32)^5 & := (-57 + 73 + 53 + 39 + 2 + 32)^5 \\
 &:= (5 + 77 - 3 + 5 + 33 - 9 + 2 + 32)^5 & := (-57 + 7 + 35 + 33 + 92 + 32)^5 \\
 &:= (-5 + 77 + 3 - 5 + 3 + 39 - 2 + 32)^5 & := (-5 + 773 - 533 - 92 - 3 + 2)^5 \\
 &:= (5 - 7 + 73 + 53 - 3 - 9 - 2 + 32)^5 & \mathbf{57736239625} := (-57 - 7 - 36 - 2 + 3962 + 5)^3
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 \mathbf{57915683909} &:= (-57+9+1+5-6+8+3909)^3 & := (-5-9+5+535-6-9-2-9-6)^4 \\
 &:= (-57+9-1-5+6+8+3909)^3 & := (-59+5-5-3+569+2-9-6)^4 \\
 &:= (5-7-9-15-6-8+3909)^3 & := (-59-5+5-3+569+2-9-6)^4 \\
 &:= (5-7+9+1-56+8+3909)^3 & := (5-95+5-3+569-2+9+6)^4 \\
 &:= (-5-7-91-5+68+3909)^3 & := (5-95-5+3+569+2+9+6)^4 \\
 \mathbf{58120048561} &:= (581-2+004-85-6-1)^4 & := (-5-95+5+3+569+2+9+6)^4 \\
 &:= (5-81+2-004+8+561)^4 & := (5+9+553-5-69-2+9-6)^4 \\
 &:= (5+8-12+00485+6-1)^4 & := (-5+9+553+5-69-2+9-6)^4 \\
 &:= (-5-8+12+00485+6+1)^4 & := (5-9+553-5-6-9-29-6)^4 \\
 &:= (581-20+04-8-5-61)^4 & := (-5-9+553+5-6-9-29-6)^4 \\
 &:= (-58+1+2+00485+61)^4 & := (5-9-55-3+569+2-9-6)^4 \\
 &:= (-5-81+20+04-8+561)^4 & := (5+9-5+535-6-9-29-6)^4 \\
 &:= (5-8+1-20-048+561)^4 & := (-5+9+5+535-6-9-29-6)^4 \\
 \mathbf{58594980096} &:= (5+8+5-9+498-009-6)^4 & := (5-9-5+535-6+9-29-6)^4 \\
 &:= (-5-8-5+9+498+009-6)^4 & := (-5-9+5+535-6+9-29-6)^4 \\
 &:= (-585+94+980+09-6)^4 & := (5-9-5-53+569+2-9-6)^4 \\
 \mathbf{58637179125} &:= (58-6+3717+91+25)^3 & := (-5-9+5-53+569+2-9-6)^4 \\
 &:= (58-6+3717-9+125)^3 & := (595-53-56+9+2-9+6)^4 \\
 \mathbf{59072816401} &:= (590-7+2-81-6-4-01)^4 & := (595-53-56-9+2+9+6)^4 \\
 &:= (5+9-07-2+81+6+401)^4 & := (595+5-35+6-92+9+6)^4 \\
 &:= (5-9+07+2+81+6+401)^4 & := (595+5+3-5-69-29-6)^4 \\
 &:= (590-7-28+1-64+01)^4 & := (595-5+3+5-69-29-6)^4 \\
 &:= (59+07+2+8+16+401)^4 & := (59+553-5-6-92-9-6)^4 \\
 &:= (5-90-72+8+1+640+1)^4 & := (59+553-5-6-9-2-96)^4 \\
 &:= (5+90+7-2+8-16+401)^4 & := (59-5+535-6-92+9-6)^4 \\
 &:= (5-9+072+8+16+401)^4 & := (59-5+535-6+9-2-96)^4 \\
 &:= (5+90+72-81+6+401)^4 & := (59-5-5+356+92-9+6)^4 \\
 \mathbf{59273381699} &:= (59+2+7-3+3816+9+9)^3 & := (59-5-5+356-9+2+96)^4 \\
 &:= (5+92+7-3+3816-9-9)^3 & := (-59+5+5-3+569-29+6)^4 \\
 &:= (-5+92-7+3+3816+9-9)^3 & := (5-95-5-3+569+29-6)^4 \\
 &:= (-5+92-7+3+3816-9+9)^3 & := (-5-95+5-3+569+29-6)^4 \\
 &:= (5-9-2-7-3+3816+99)^3 & := (5-9+5-53+569-29+6)^4 \\
 &:= (-5-9+2-7+3+3816+99)^3 & := (-59+5-53+5+692-96)^4 \\
 &:= (59+27-3+3816+9-9)^3 & := (5+95-535+6+929-6)^4 \\
 &:= (59+27-3+3816-9+9)^3 & := (5+95-535-6+929+6)^4 \\
 &:= (5+9-27-3+3816+99)^3 & := (5-95+5-356+929+6)^4 \\
 &:= (59-2-73+3816+99)^3 & \\
 \mathbf{59553569296} &:= (5-9-5+535-6-9-2-9-6)^4 & \mathbf{59638983643} := (-5-9-6+3898+36-4-3)^3 \\
 & & := (5-9+6+3898-36+43)^3
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 \mathbf{59730618429} &:= (-5 + 9 - 7 + 3061 + 842 + 9)^3 & & := (-59 + 7 + 97 + 10 + 89 - 4 + 3)^5 \\
 \mathbf{59797108943} &:= (5 + 97 + 9 + 7 + 1 + 08 + 9 + 4 + 3)^5 & & := (-5 + 9 - 797 + 1 - 08 + 943)^5 \\
 &:= (5 + 9 + 7 + 97 + 1 + 08 + 9 + 4 + 3)^5 & & := (5 + 97 + 97 - 108 + 9 + 43)^5 \\
 &:= (5 + 9 + 7 + 9 + 7 + 1 + 08 + 94 + 3)^5 & & := (5 + 97 + 97 - 10 - 89 + 43)^5 \\
 &:= (59 - 7 + 9 - 7 - 1 + 089 + 4 - 3)^5 & & := (59 - 797 - 10 + 894 - 3)^5 \\
 &:= (59 - 7 + 9 - 7 + 1 + 089 - 4 + 3)^5 & & \\
 &:= (59 + 7 + 9 + 7 + 1 + 08 + 9 + 43)^5 & & \\
 &:= (5 + 97 + 9 + 7 - 1 - 08 - 9 + 43)^5 & & \\
 &:= (5 + 97 - 9 + 7 + 1 + 08 - 9 + 43)^5 & & \\
 &:= (5 + 97 - 9 + 7 - 1 - 08 + 9 + 43)^5 & & \\
 &:= (5 + 9 + 79 + 7 + 1 + 08 - 9 + 43)^5 & & \\
 &:= (5 + 9 + 79 + 7 - 1 - 08 + 9 + 43)^5 & & \\
 &:= (5 - 9 + 79 + 7 + 1 + 08 + 9 + 43)^5 & & \\
 &:= (5 + 9 + 7 + 97 - 1 - 08 - 9 + 43)^5 & & \\
 &:= (5 - 9 + 7 + 97 + 1 + 08 - 9 + 43)^5 & & \\
 &:= (5 - 9 + 7 + 97 - 1 - 08 + 9 + 43)^5 & & \\
 &:= (-5 - 9 + 7 - 9 + 71 + 089 - 4 + 3)^5 & & \\
 &:= (5 + 9 + 7 + 9 + 71 + 08 - 9 + 43)^5 & & \\
 &:= (5 + 9 + 7 - 9 + 71 + 08 + 9 + 43)^5 & & \\
 &:= (5 - 9 + 7 + 9 + 71 + 08 + 9 + 43)^5 & & \\
 &:= (-5 + 9 + 7 + 9 + 7 + 108 + 9 - 4 + 3)^5 & & \\
 &:= (5 + 9 + 7 + 9 + 7 + 108 - 9 + 4 + 3)^5 & & \\
 &:= (5 + 9 + 7 - 9 + 7 + 108 + 9 + 4 + 3)^5 & & \\
 &:= (5 - 9 + 7 + 9 + 7 + 108 + 9 + 4 + 3)^5 & & \\
 &:= (5 + 9 + 7 + 9 + 7 + 10 + 89 + 4 + 3)^5 & & \\
 &:= (59 + 79 - 7 + 10 - 8 + 9 + 4 - 3)^5 & & \\
 &:= (59 + 79 + 7 - 10 - 8 + 9 + 4 + 3)^5 & & \\
 &:= (59 - 7 + 97 + 10 - 8 - 9 + 4 - 3)^5 & & \\
 &:= (59 + 7 + 97 - 10 - 8 - 9 + 4 + 3)^5 & & \\
 &:= (-59 + 7 + 97 - 1 + 08 + 94 - 3)^5 & & \\
 &:= (59 + 7 - 9 - 7 + 10 - 8 + 94 - 3)^5 & & \\
 &:= (59 - 7 - 9 + 7 + 10 - 8 + 94 - 3)^5 & & \\
 &:= (59 - 7 + 9 - 7 - 10 + 8 + 94 - 3)^5 & & \\
 &:= (59 + 7 - 9 + 7 - 10 - 8 + 94 + 3)^5 & & \\
 &:= (5 - 9 + 7 - 9 + 7 + 108 - 9 + 43)^5 & & \\
 &:= (5 - 9 + 7 - 9 + 7 + 10 + 89 + 43)^5 & & \\
 &:= (-59 + 79 + 7 + 108 + 9 - 4 + 3)^5 & & \\
 &:= (-59 + 7 + 97 + 108 - 9 - 4 + 3)^5 & & \\
 & & & \mathbf{60037250625} := (-6 - 003 + 7 - 2 + 506 - 2 - 5)^4 \\
 & & & := (-6 + 003 - 7 + 2 + 506 + 2 - 5)^4 \\
 & & & := (-6 - 003 - 7 + 2 + 506 - 2 + 5)^4 \\
 & & & := (-6 - 003 - 7 - 2 + 506 + 2 + 5)^4 \\
 & & & := (6 + 003 + 7 - 2 + 506 - 25)^4 \\
 & & & := (600 + 3 - 72 - 5 - 06 - 25)^4 \\
 & & & := (600 + 3 + 7 + 2 - 50 - 62 - 5)^4 \\
 & & & := (600 - 3 + 7 - 2 - 50 - 62 + 5)^4 \\
 & & & := (60 + 0372 + 50 + 6 + 2 + 5)^4 \\
 & & & := (-60 - 03 - 72 + 5 + 0625)^4 \\
 & & & := (6 + 00372 + 50 + 62 + 5)^4 \\
 & & & \mathbf{60182393041} := (6018 + 239304 - 1)^2 \\
 & & & \mathbf{60328533448} := (603 - 28 - 5 + 3344 + 8)^3 \\
 & & & \mathbf{60424522596} := (604 + 245225 - 9 - 6)^2 \\
 & & & \mathbf{60523872256} := (605 - 23 - 87 + 2 - 2 - 5 + 6)^4 \\
 & & & := (605 - 23 - 87 - 2 + 2 - 5 + 6)^4 \\
 & & & := (605 + 2 - 38 - 72 - 2 - 5 + 6)^4 \\
 & & & := (605 - 2 - 38 - 72 + 2 - 5 + 6)^4 \\
 & & & := (605 - 2 + 3 - 87 - 22 + 5 - 6)^4 \\
 & & & := (605 + 2 - 3 - 87 - 22 - 5 + 6)^4 \\
 & & & := (605 + 2 - 3 - 87 - 2 - 25 + 6)^4 \\
 & & & := (605 - 2 - 3 - 87 + 2 - 25 + 6)^4 \\
 & & & := (60 + 52 + 387 - 2 - 2 - 5 + 6)^4 \\
 & & & := (60 - 5 + 2 + 387 - 2 - 2 + 56)^4 \\
 & & & := (60 - 5 - 2 + 387 + 2 - 2 + 56)^4 \\
 & & & := (60 - 5 - 2 + 387 - 2 + 2 + 56)^4 \\
 & & & := (6 + 0523 + 8 - 72 + 25 + 6)^4 \\
 & & & := (6 + 0523 + 8 - 7 + 22 - 56)^4 \\
 & & & := (6 + 05 - 238 + 722 - 5 + 6)^4 \\
 & & & := (6 - 05 - 238 + 722 + 5 + 6)^4 \\
 & & & := (6 + 05 + 238 - 7 - 2 + 256)^4 \\
 & & & := (-60 + 523 - 8 + 72 - 25 - 6)^4 \\
 & & & := (-60 + 523 - 8 + 7 - 22 + 56)^4
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} & := (605 + 23 + 87 - 225 + 6)^4 \\ \mathbf{60782464681} & := (-6 + 078 + 246468 + 1)^2 \\ \mathbf{60837567237} & := (60 + 8 + 3756 + 72 + 37)^3 \\ \mathbf{61013446081} & := (-6 + 1 + 01 + 34 + 460 + 8 - 1)^4 \\ & := (-6 + 1 - 01 + 34 + 460 + 8 + 1)^4 \\ & := (-6 - 1 + 01 + 34 + 460 + 8 + 1)^4 \\ & := (610 + 1 - 3 - 44 - 60 - 8 + 1)^4 \\ & := (61 - 013 - 4 + 460 - 8 + 1)^4 \\ & := (61 + 01 - 34 + 460 + 8 + 1)^4 \\ & := (-6 - 101 - 3 + 4 - 4 + 608 - 1)^4 \\ & := (-6 - 101 - 3 - 4 + 4 + 608 - 1)^4 \\ & := (-6 - 101 + 3 - 4 - 4 + 608 + 1)^4 \\ & := (-61 + 013 + 4 + 460 + 81)^4 \\ & := (-6 - 10 + 134 + 460 - 81)^4 \\ \mathbf{61023377953} & := (6 + 102 - 3 + 3779 + 53)^3 \\ \mathbf{61116425019} & := (-6 - 1116 + 42 + 5019)^3 \\ \mathbf{61162984000} & := (-61 + 16 + 2 - 9 - 8 + 4000)^3 \\ & := (-6 - 11 - 6 - 29 - 8 + 4000)^3 \\ & := (-6 - 1 - 16 - 29 - 8 + 4000)^3 \\ \mathbf{61396133625} & := (-6 - 1 + 3961 + 3 - 3 - 6 + 2 - 5)^3 \\ & := (-6 - 1 + 3961 - 3 + 3 - 6 + 2 - 5)^3 \\ & := (-6 - 1 + 3961 - 3 - 3 - 6 - 2 + 5)^3 \\ \mathbf{61442834536} & := (61 + 4428 - 3 - 4 - 536)^3 \\ \mathbf{61505984016} & := (6 - 1 + 505 - 9 + 8 - 4 - 01 - 6)^4 \\ & := (-6 + 1 + 505 + 9 - 8 + 4 - 01 - 6)^4 \\ & := (-6 - 1 + 505 + 9 - 8 + 4 + 01 - 6)^4 \\ & := (-6 + 1 + 505 - 9 + 8 + 4 + 01 - 6)^4 \\ & := (-6 - 1 + 505 - 9 + 8 - 4 - 01 + 6)^4 \\ & := (6 + 1 + 505 - 9 - 8 - 4 + 01 + 6)^4 \\ & := (6 - 1 + 5 - 05 + 98 + 401 - 6)^4 \\ & := (6 - 1 - 5 + 05 + 98 + 401 - 6)^4 \\ & := (-6 + 1 + 5 + 05 + 98 + 401 - 6)^4 \\ & := (-6 - 1 + 5 - 05 + 98 + 401 + 6)^4 \\ & := (-6 - 1 - 5 + 05 + 98 + 401 + 6)^4 \\ & := (61 + 505 + 9 - 84 + 01 + 6)^4 \\ & := (-61 - 50 + 598 + 4 + 01 + 6)^4 \\ & := (-6 + 1 - 50 + 598 - 40 + 1 - 6)^4 \\ & := (615 + 05 - 98 - 40 + 16)^4 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} & := (-6 - 150 + 598 + 40 + 16)^4 \\ \mathbf{61917364224} & := (6 + 19 + 1 + 7 - 3 - 6 - 4 - 2 - 2 - 4)^{10} \\ & := (-6 + 19 + 1 + 7 - 3 + 6 - 4 - 2 - 2 - 4)^{10} \\ & := (6 + 19 + 1 - 7 + 3 - 6 + 4 - 2 - 2 - 4)^{10} \\ & := (-6 + 19 - 1 + 7 + 3 - 6 + 4 - 2 - 2 - 4)^{10} \\ & := (-6 + 19 + 1 - 7 + 3 + 6 + 4 - 2 - 2 - 4)^{10} \\ & := (6 + 19 - 1 - 7 - 3 + 6 - 4 + 2 - 2 - 4)^{10} \\ & := (-6 + 19 + 1 + 7 - 3 - 6 + 4 + 2 - 2 - 4)^{10} \\ & := (6 + 19 - 1 - 7 - 3 + 6 - 4 - 2 + 2 - 4)^{10} \\ & := (-6 + 19 + 1 + 7 - 3 - 6 + 4 - 2 + 2 - 4)^{10} \\ & := (6 + 19 + 1 - 7 + 3 - 6 - 4 + 2 + 2 - 4)^{10} \\ & := (-6 + 19 - 1 + 7 + 3 - 6 - 4 + 2 + 2 - 4)^{10} \\ & := (-6 + 19 + 1 - 7 + 3 + 6 - 4 + 2 + 2 - 4)^{10} \\ & := (6 + 19 - 1 - 7 - 3 - 6 + 4 + 2 + 2 - 4)^{10} \\ & := (-6 + 19 - 1 - 7 - 3 + 6 + 4 + 2 + 2 - 4)^{10} \\ & := (6 + 19 + 1 - 7 + 3 - 6 - 4 - 2 - 2 + 4)^{10} \\ & := (-6 + 19 - 1 + 7 + 3 - 6 - 4 - 2 - 2 + 4)^{10} \\ & := (-6 + 19 + 1 - 7 + 3 + 6 - 4 - 2 - 2 + 4)^{10} \\ & := (6 + 19 - 1 - 7 - 3 - 6 + 4 - 2 - 2 + 4)^{10} \\ & := (-6 + 19 - 1 - 7 - 3 + 6 + 4 - 2 - 2 + 4)^{10} \\ & := (-6 + 19 + 1 + 7 - 3 - 6 - 4 + 2 - 2 + 4)^{10} \\ & := (-6 + 19 + 1 - 7 + 3 - 6 + 4 + 2 - 2 + 4)^{10} \\ & := (6 - 19 + 1 + 7 + 3 + 6 + 4 + 2 - 2 + 4)^{10} \\ & := (-6 + 19 + 1 + 7 - 3 - 6 - 4 - 2 + 2 + 4)^{10} \\ & := (-6 + 19 + 1 - 7 + 3 - 6 + 4 - 2 + 2 + 4)^{10} \\ & := (6 - 19 + 1 + 7 + 3 + 6 + 4 - 2 + 2 + 4)^{10} \\ & := (6 + 19 - 1 - 7 - 3 - 6 - 4 + 2 + 2 + 4)^{10} \\ & := (-6 + 19 - 1 - 7 - 3 + 6 - 4 + 2 + 2 + 4)^{10} \\ & := (6 + 1 + 9 + 17 - 3 - 6 - 4 - 2 - 2 - 4)^{10} \\ & := (-6 + 1 + 9 + 17 - 3 + 6 - 4 - 2 - 2 - 4)^{10} \\ & := (6 + 1 - 9 + 17 + 3 - 6 + 4 - 2 - 2 - 4)^{10} \\ & := (-6 - 1 + 9 + 17 + 3 - 6 + 4 - 2 - 2 - 4)^{10} \\ & := (6 - 1 - 9 + 17 - 3 + 6 + 4 - 2 - 2 - 4)^{10} \\ & := (-6 + 1 + 9 + 17 - 3 - 6 + 4 + 2 - 2 - 4)^{10} \\ & := (6 + 1 - 9 + 17 + 3 - 6 + 4 + 2 - 2 - 4)^{10} \\ & := (-6 + 1 - 9 + 17 + 3 + 6 + 4 + 2 - 2 - 4)^{10} \\ & := (-6 + 1 + 9 + 17 - 3 - 6 + 4 - 2 + 2 - 4)^{10} \\ & := (6 + 1 - 9 + 17 + 3 - 6 + 4 - 2 + 2 - 4)^{10} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} & := (-6+1-9+17+3+6+4-2+2-4)^{10} & := (-61+9+1+73-6-4+2+2-4)^{10} \\ & := (-6-1+9+17+3-6-4+2+2-4)^{10} & := (61+9-1+73+6-4+2+2-4)^5 \\ & := (6-1-9+17-3+6-4+2+2-4)^{10} & := (-61-9-1+73+6+4+2+2-4)^{10} \\ & := (6+1+9-17+3+6+4+2+2-4)^{10} & := (-61+9+1+73-6-4-2-2+4)^{10} \\ & := (-6-1+9+17+3-6-4-2-2+4)^{10} & := (61+9-1+73+6-4-2-2+4)^5 \\ & := (6-1-9+17-3+6-4-2-2+4)^{10} & := (-61-9-1+73+6+4-2-2+4)^{10} \\ & := (6+1+9-17+3+6+4-2-2+4)^{10} & := (61+9-1+73-6+4+2-2+4)^5 \\ & := (-6+1+9+17-3-6-4+2-2+4)^{10} & := (61+9+1-73+6+4+2-2+4)^{10} \\ & := (6+1-9+17+3-6-4+2-2+4)^{10} & := (61+9-1+73-6+4-2+2+4)^5 \\ & := (-6+1-9+17+3+6-4+2-2+4)^{10} & := (61+9+1-73+6+4-2+2+4)^{10} \\ & := (6-1-9+17-3-6+4+2-2+4)^{10} & := (-61-9-1+73+6-4+2+2+4)^{10} \\ & := (-6-1-9+17-3+6+4+2-2+4)^{10} & := (61-9+1+73+6+4+2+2+4)^5 \\ & := (-6+1+9+17-3-6-4-2+2+4)^{10} & := (61-9+1+7-36-4-2-2-4)^{10} \\ & := (6+1-9+17+3-6-4-2+2+4)^{10} & := (61-9-1-7-36+4+2+2-4)^{10} \\ & := (-6+1-9+17+3+6-4-2+2+4)^{10} & := (61-9-1-7-36+4-2-2+4)^{10} \\ & := (6-1-9+17-3-6+4-2+2+4)^{10} & := (61-9-1-7-36-4+2+2+4)^{10} \\ & := (-6-1-9+17-3+6+4-2+2+4)^{10} & := (6-19-1-7+3-6+42-2-4)^{10} \\ & := (6+1+9-17+3+6-4+2+2+4)^{10} & := (-6-19-1-7+3+6+42-2-4)^{10} \\ & := (-6+1-9+17+3-6+4+2+2+4)^{10} & := (6-19+1-7-3-6+42+2-4)^{10} \\ & := (6-1+9-17-3+6+4+2+2+4)^{10} & := (-6-19-1+7-3-6+42+2-4)^{10} \\ & := (6-1-9-1-7+36-4-2-2-4)^{10} & := (-6-19+1-7-3+6+42+2-4)^{10} \\ & := (-6+1-9+1-7+36+4-2-2-4)^{10} & := (-6-19-1-7+3-6+42+2+4)^{10} \\ & := (-6-1-9-1-7+36+4+2-2-4)^{10} & := (6+19+1+7+3+6-4-22-4)^{10} \\ & := (-6-1-9-1-7+36+4-2+2-4)^{10} & := (6+19-1+7-3+6+4-22-4)^{10} \\ & := (-6+1-9+1-7+36-4+2+2-4)^{10} & := (-6+19+1-7-3-6-4+22-4)^{10} \\ & := (-6+1-9+1-7+36-4-2-2+4)^{10} & := (6-19+1+7-3+6-4+22-4)^{10} \\ & := (-6-1-9-1-7+36-4+2-2+4)^{10} & := (6-19-1+7+3-6+4+22-4)^{10} \\ & := (-6-1-9-1-7+36-4-2+2+4)^{10} & := (6-19+1-7+3+6+4+22-4)^{10} \\ & := (61+91+7+3-6-4-2-2-4)^5 & := (-6-19-1+7+3+6+4+22-4)^{10} \\ & := (61+91-7-3+6+4-2-2-4)^5 & := (6+19-1+7-3+6-4-22+4)^{10} \\ & := (-61+91-7+3-6-4+2-2-4)^{10} & := (6+19-1-7+3+6+4-22+4)^{10} \\ & := (-61+91-7+3-6-4-2+2-4)^{10} & := (6-19-1+7+3-6-4+22+4)^{10} \\ & := (61+91-7-3+6-4+2+2-4)^5 & := (6-19+1-7+3+6-4+22+4)^{10} \\ & := (61+91-7-3+6-4-2-2+4)^5 & := (-6-19-1+7+3+6-4+22+4)^{10} \\ & := (61+91-7-3-6+4+2-2+4)^5 & := (6-19-1-7-3+6+4+22+4)^{10} \\ & := (61+91-7-3-6+4-2+2+4)^5 & := (6+19+1+7+3+6-4-2-24)^{10} \\ & := (-61+9+1+73-6+4-2-2-4)^{10} & := (6+19-1+7-3+6+4-2-24)^{10} \\ & := (61+9-1+73+6+4-2-2-4)^5 & := (6+19+1+7+3-6+4+2-24)^{10} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} & := (-6 + 19 + 1 + 7 + 3 + 6 + 4 + 2 - 24)^{10} & := (6 + 1 + 9 - 17 - 3 - 6 - 4 + 22 + 4)^{10} \\ & := (6 - 19 + 1 + 7 - 3 - 6 + 4 - 2 + 24)^{10} & := (-6 + 1 + 9 - 17 - 3 + 6 - 4 + 22 + 4)^{10} \\ & := (-6 - 19 + 1 + 7 - 3 + 6 + 4 - 2 + 24)^{10} & := (6 + 1 - 9 - 17 + 3 + 6 - 4 + 22 + 4)^{10} \\ & := (6 - 19 - 1 + 7 + 3 - 6 - 4 + 2 + 24)^{10} & := (-6 - 1 + 9 - 17 + 3 - 6 + 4 + 22 + 4)^{10} \\ & := (6 - 19 + 1 - 7 + 3 + 6 - 4 + 2 + 24)^{10} & := (6 - 1 - 9 - 17 - 3 + 6 + 4 + 22 + 4)^{10} \\ & := (-6 - 19 - 1 + 7 + 3 + 6 - 4 + 2 + 24)^{10} & := (6 + 1 + 9 + 17 + 3 + 6 - 4 - 2 - 24)^{10} \\ & := (6 - 19 - 1 - 7 - 3 + 6 + 4 + 2 + 24)^{10} & := (6 - 1 + 9 + 17 - 3 + 6 + 4 - 2 - 24)^{10} \\ & := (6 + 1 + 91 - 7 - 3 + 64 - 2 - 2 - 4)^5 & := (6 + 1 + 9 + 17 + 3 - 6 + 4 + 2 - 24)^{10} \\ & := (-6 - 1 + 91 + 7 - 3 + 64 - 2 - 2 - 4)^5 & := (-6 + 1 + 9 + 17 + 3 + 6 + 4 + 2 - 24)^{10} \\ & := (-6 - 1 + 91 - 7 + 3 - 64 + 2 - 2 - 4)^{10} & := (-6 + 1 - 9 + 17 - 3 - 6 - 4 - 2 + 24)^{10} \\ & := (-6 - 1 + 91 - 7 + 3 - 64 - 2 + 2 - 4)^{10} & := (6 - 1 + 9 - 17 + 3 - 6 - 4 - 2 + 24)^{10} \\ & := (-6 + 1 + 91 - 7 - 3 - 64 + 2 + 2 - 4)^{10} & := (-6 - 1 + 9 - 17 + 3 + 6 - 4 - 2 + 24)^{10} \\ & := (-6 - 1 + 91 - 7 + 3 + 64 + 2 + 2 - 4)^5 & := (6 + 1 + 9 - 17 - 3 - 6 - 4 + 2 + 24)^{10} \\ & := (-6 + 1 + 91 - 7 - 3 - 64 - 2 - 2 + 4)^{10} & := (-6 + 1 + 9 - 17 - 3 + 6 - 4 + 2 + 24)^{10} \\ & := (-6 - 1 + 91 - 7 + 3 + 64 - 2 - 2 + 4)^5 & := (6 + 1 - 9 - 17 + 3 + 6 - 4 + 2 + 24)^{10} \\ & := (-6 + 1 + 91 - 7 - 3 + 64 + 2 - 2 + 4)^5 & := (-6 - 1 + 9 - 17 + 3 - 6 + 4 + 2 + 24)^{10} \\ & := (-6 + 1 + 91 - 7 - 3 + 64 - 2 + 2 + 4)^5 & := (6 - 1 - 9 - 17 - 3 + 6 + 4 + 2 + 24)^{10} \\ & := (6 + 1 + 91 + 7 - 3 + 6 + 42 - 2 - 4)^5 & := (6 + 1 + 9 - 1 + 73 + 64 - 2 - 2 - 4)^5 \\ & := (6 - 1 + 91 + 7 + 3 - 6 + 42 - 2 + 4)^5 & := (6 - 1 + 9 + 1 + 73 + 64 - 2 - 2 - 4)^5 \\ & := (6 + 1 + 91 - 7 + 3 + 6 + 42 - 2 + 4)^5 & := (-6 + 1 + 9 - 1 + 73 - 64 + 2 + 2 - 4)^{10} \\ & := (-6 - 1 + 91 + 7 + 3 + 6 + 42 - 2 + 4)^5 & := (-6 - 1 + 9 + 1 + 73 - 64 + 2 + 2 - 4)^{10} \\ & := (6 + 1 + 91 + 7 - 3 - 6 + 42 + 2 + 4)^5 & := (-6 + 1 + 9 - 1 + 73 - 64 - 2 - 2 + 4)^{10} \\ & := (-6 + 1 + 91 + 7 - 3 + 6 + 42 + 2 + 4)^5 & := (-6 - 1 + 9 + 1 + 73 - 64 - 2 - 2 + 4)^{10} \\ & := (6 + 1 + 91 + 7 + 3 + 6 + 4 + 22 + 4)^5 & := (6 + 1 - 9 + 1 + 73 - 64 + 2 - 2 + 4)^{10} \\ & := (6 + 1 + 91 + 7 + 3 + 6 + 4 + 2 + 24)^5 & := (6 + 1 + 9 + 1 - 73 + 64 + 2 - 2 + 4)^{10} \\ & := (-6 - 1 + 9 - 17 - 3 - 6 + 42 - 2 - 4)^{10} & := (-6 + 1 + 9 - 1 + 73 + 64 + 2 - 2 + 4)^5 \\ & := (6 - 1 - 9 - 17 + 3 - 6 + 42 - 2 - 4)^{10} & := (-6 - 1 + 9 + 1 + 73 + 64 + 2 - 2 + 4)^5 \\ & := (-6 - 1 - 9 - 17 + 3 + 6 + 42 - 2 - 4)^{10} & := (6 + 1 - 9 + 1 + 73 - 64 - 2 + 2 + 4)^{10} \\ & := (6 + 1 - 9 - 17 - 3 - 6 + 42 + 2 - 4)^{10} & := (6 + 1 + 9 + 1 - 73 + 64 - 2 + 2 + 4)^{10} \\ & := (-6 + 1 - 9 - 17 - 3 + 6 + 42 + 2 - 4)^{10} & := (-6 + 1 + 9 - 1 + 73 + 64 - 2 + 2 + 4)^5 \\ & := (-6 - 1 - 9 - 17 + 3 - 6 + 42 + 2 + 4)^{10} & := (-6 - 1 + 9 + 1 + 73 + 64 - 2 + 2 + 4)^5 \\ & := (6 + 1 + 9 + 17 + 3 + 6 - 4 - 22 - 4)^{10} & := (6 - 1 - 9 - 1 + 73 - 64 + 2 + 2 + 4)^{10} \\ & := (6 - 1 + 9 + 17 - 3 + 6 + 4 - 22 - 4)^{10} & := (6 - 1 + 9 - 1 - 73 + 64 + 2 + 2 + 4)^{10} \\ & := (-6 - 1 - 9 + 17 + 3 - 6 - 4 + 22 - 4)^{10} & := (6 + 1 - 9 + 1 + 73 + 64 + 2 + 2 + 4)^5 \\ & := (6 + 1 + 9 - 17 - 3 - 6 + 4 + 22 - 4)^{10} & := (-6 + 1 - 9 - 1 + 73 - 6 - 42 - 2 + 4)^{10} \\ & := (-6 + 1 + 9 - 17 - 3 + 6 + 4 + 22 - 4)^{10} & := (-6 - 1 - 9 + 1 + 73 - 6 - 42 - 2 + 4)^{10} \\ & := (6 + 1 - 9 - 17 + 3 + 6 + 4 + 22 - 4)^{10} & := (6 + 1 + 9 + 1 + 73 + 6 + 42 + 2 + 4)^5 \\ & := (6 - 1 + 9 + 17 - 3 + 6 - 4 - 22 + 4)^{10} & := (6 + 1 + 9 + 1 + 7 + 36 - 42 - 2 - 4)^{10} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} & := (-6+1+9+1+7-36+42-2-4)^{10} & := (61-9+17+3+64+2+2+4)^5 \\ & := (6-1+9-1+7+36-42+2-4)^{10} & := (61-9+17-3-6-42-2-4)^{10} \\ & := (6+1+9-1-7-36+42+2-4)^{10} & := (61+9-17-3+6-42+2-4)^{10} \\ & := (6-1+9+1-7-36+42+2-4)^{10} & := (-61+9+17-3+6+42-2+4)^{10} \\ & := (-6-1+9-1+7-36+42+2-4)^{10} & := (61+9+17+3+6+42+2+4)^5 \\ & := (6+1-9-1+7-36+42-2+4)^{10} & := (61-9-17-3-6+4-22+4)^{10} \\ & := (6-1-9+1+7-36+42-2+4)^{10} & := (61-9-17-3+6-4+2-24)^{10} \\ & := (-6+1+9+1+7+36-42+2+4)^{10} & := (61-9-1-73-6+42+2-4)^{10} \\ & := (6-1+9-1-7+36-4-22-4)^{10} & := (-61-9+1+73-6-4+22-4)^{10} \\ & := (6+1-9+1+7+36-4-22-4)^{10} & := (61-9-1+73+6-4+22-4)^5 \\ & := (-6+1+9+1-7+36+4-22-4)^{10} & := (61+9-1-73-6+4+22-4)^{10} \\ & := (-6+1+9+1-7+36-4-22+4)^{10} & := (-61+9-1+73+6+4-22+4)^{10} \\ & := (6+1-9-1-7+36+4-22+4)^{10} & := (61+9-1-73-6-4+22+4)^{10} \\ & := (6-1-9+1-7+36+4-22+4)^{10} & := (61-9-1+73-6+4-2+24)^5 \\ & := (-6-1-9-1+7+36+4-22+4)^{10} & := (61-9+1-73+6+4-2+24)^{10} \\ & := (6-1+9-1-7+36-4-2-24)^{10} & := (61+9-1-73-6-4+2+24)^{10} \\ & := (6+1-9+1+7+36-4-2-24)^{10} & := (-61+9-1-7+36+42-2-4)^{10} \\ & := (-6+1+9+1-7+36+4-2-24)^{10} & := (-61-9-1+7+36+42+2-4)^{10} \\ & := (6-1-9-1+7+36-4+2-24)^{10} & := (61+9+1-7+36+42-2+4)^5 \\ & := (-6-1+9-1-7+36+4+2-24)^{10} & := (61-9+1+7+36+42+2+4)^5 \\ & := (-6+1-9+1+7+36+4+2-24)^{10} & := (61+9+1+7-36-4-22-4)^{10} \\ & := (6+1+9-1+7-36+4-2+24)^{10} & := (-61+9-1+7+36+4+22-4)^{10} \\ & := (6-1+9+1+7-36+4-2+24)^{10} & := (61+9-1-7-36+4-22+4)^{10} \\ & := (61-91-7+3+6+42+2-4)^{10} & := (-61+9-1+7+36-4+22+4)^{10} \\ & := (61-91+7-3-6+42-2+4)^{10} & := (61+9+1+7+36+4+22+4)^5 \\ & := (-61+91+7+3-6+4-22-4)^{10} & := (61+9+1+7-36-4-2-24)^{10} \\ & := (-61+91+7+3-6-4-22+4)^{10} & := (-61+9-1+7+36-4+2+24)^{10} \\ & := (-61+91-7-3+6+4-22+4)^{10} & := (61+9+1+7+36+4+2+24)^5 \\ & := (-61+91+7+3-6+4-2-24)^{10} & := (-6+191+7-36-4-2-2-4)^5 \\ & := (61+91+7-3+6+4+2-24)^5 & := (-6-19+1-7-3+64-22+4)^{10} \\ & := (61-91+7+3+6+4-2+24)^{10} & := (-6-19-1-7+3+64+2-24)^{10} \\ & := (61+9+17-3-64-2-2-4)^{10} & := (6+19+1+7+3-6-42+24)^{10} \\ & := (61+9+17-3+64+2-2-4)^5 & := (-6+19+1+7+3+6-42+24)^{10} \\ & := (61+9+17-3+64-2+2-4)^5 & := (6+1+91+7-3-64-22-4)^{10} \\ & := (61-9+17+3-64+2-2+4)^{10} & := (6-1+91+7+3+64-22-4)^5 \\ & := (-61-9+17-3+64+2-2+4)^{10} & := (6+1+91-7+3-64-22+4)^{10} \\ & := (61-9+17+3-64-2+2+4)^{10} & := (-6-1+91+7+3-64-22+4)^{10} \\ & := (-61-9+17-3+64-2+2+4)^{10} & := (6+1+91+7-3-64-2-24)^{10} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} &:= (6-1+91+7+3+64-2-24)^5 & &:= (61+9+17-3-6-42-24)^{10} \\ &:= (6+1+91+7-3+64+2-24)^5 & &:= (61-9+17+3+6-42-24)^{10} \\ &:= (6+1-91+7+3+64-2+24)^{10} & &:= (61+9+17-3-6+42+24)^5 \\ &:= (6-1-91+7-3+6-4+224)^5 & &:= (61-9+17+3+6+42+24)^5 \\ &:= (6-1-91-7+3+6+4+224)^5 & &:= (-61-9-17-3+6+4+224)^5 \\ &:= (-6+1-9-17-3+64-22+4)^{10} & &:= (6+191-73+6-4+22-4)^5 \\ &:= (-6-1-9-17+3+64+2-24)^{10} & &:= (6+191-73-6+4-2+24)^5 \\ &:= (-6+1-9+17-3-6+42-24)^{10} & &:= (-6+191-73+6+4-2+24)^5 \\ &:= (6-1+9-17+3-6+42-24)^{10} & &:= (6+19+173-6-42-2-4)^5 \\ &:= (-6-1+9-17+3+6+42-24)^{10} & &:= (-6+19+173+6-42-2-4)^5 \\ &:= (6+1+9+17+3-6-42+24)^{10} & &:= (-6+19+173-6-42+2+4)^5 \\ &:= (-6+1+9+17+3+6-42+24)^{10} & &:= (6-19+173+6+4-22-4)^5 \\ &:= (-6+1-9-1+73-64+22-4)^{10} & &:= (6-19+173+6-4-22+4)^5 \\ &:= (-6-1-9+1+73-64+22-4)^{10} & &:= (6-19+173+6+4-2-24)^5 \\ &:= (-6+1+9-1-73+64+22-4)^{10} & &:= (6+19-17-36+42+2-4)^{10} \\ &:= (-6-1+9+1-73+64+22-4)^{10} & &:= (6-19+17-36+42-2+4)^{10} \\ &:= (6-1-9-1-73+64+22+4)^{10} & &:= (-6+19+17-36-4-2+24)^{10} \\ &:= (6+1-9+1-73+64-2+24)^{10} & &:= (-6-19-17+36-4-2+24)^{10} \\ &:= (-6+1-9-1+73+64-2+24)^5 & &:= (6-19+1-7+3-64+224)^5 \\ &:= (-6-1-9+1+73+64-2+24)^5 & &:= (-6-19-1+7+3-64+224)^5 \\ &:= (6-1-9-1-73+64+2+24)^{10} & &:= (-6+1+9-17-3-64+224)^5 \\ &:= (6+1-9+1+73+6-42-24)^{10} & &:= (6+1-9-17+3-64+224)^5 \\ &:= (6-1+9-1-73+6+42+24)^{10} & &:= (6+1-9-1+7+364-224)^5 \\ &:= (6+1-9+1+73+6+42+24)^5 & &:= (6-1-9+1+7+364-224)^5 \\ &:= (-6+1+9-1-73-6-4+224)^5 & &:= (-619+1+736+4-2+24)^5 \\ &:= (-6-1+9+1-73-6-4+224)^5 & &:= (619+1+7+3-642+24)^{10} \\ &:= (6-1-9-1-73-6+4+224)^5 & &:= (-61-91+7-3-64+224)^{10} \\ &:= (-6-1-9-1-73+6+4+224)^5 & &:= (-61-9-1-73+64+224)^5 \\ &:= (-6-1+9-1-7+36-42+24)^{10} & &:= (6+191+7+36-4-224)^{10} \\ &:= (-6+1-9+1+7+36-42+24)^{10} & &:= (-6+19+173-64-2+24)^5 \\ &:= (-619-1-7+3+642-2-4)^{10} & &:= (6+19+17+36-42-24)^{10} \\ &:= (-619+1-7-3+642+2-4)^{10} & &:= (-6+19+17-36+42-24)^{10} \\ &:= (61-91+7-3+64-22-4)^{10} & &:= (-6-19-17+36+42-24)^{10} \\ &:= (61-91-7+3+64-22+4)^{10} & &:= (6+19+17+36+42+24)^5 \\ &:= (61-91+7-3+64-2-24)^{10} & &:= (619+173-642-2-4)^5 \\ &:= (61+91+7-3+6-42+24)^5 & &:= (6+19-173-64+224)^{10} \\ &:= (61+9-17-3-64+22+4)^{10} & &:= (6-19+17+364-224)^5 \\ &:= (61+9-17-3-64+2+24)^{10} & &:= (6+2+2+4037-73-4-7)^3 \end{aligned}$$

63139882168 := (6 - 3 + 1 + 3988 - 2 - 16 + 8) ³	:= (-6 + 40 + 97 - 3 + 4 + 06 + 2 + 5) ⁵
:= (6 - 31 + 3988 + 21 + 6 - 8) ³	:= (6 + 40 + 9 + 73 + 4 + 06 + 2 + 5) ⁵
63187463087 := (-631 - 8 + 7 + 4630 - 8 - 7) ³	:= (6 - 4 + 097 + 3 + 40 + 6 + 2 - 5) ⁵
:= (-631 - 8 - 7 + 4630 - 8 + 7) ³	:= (6 - 4 + 097 - 3 + 40 + 6 - 2 + 5) ⁵
63282696625 := (6 + 3282 + 696 - 6 + 2 + 5) ³	:= (6 + 4 + 097 - 3 + 40 - 6 + 2 + 5) ⁵
:= (-6 + 3282 + 696 + 6 + 2 + 5) ³	:= (-6 + 4 + 097 - 3 + 40 + 6 + 2 + 5) ⁵
63425726272 := (6 + 3425 - 72 + 627 + 2) ³	:= (-6 + 4 + 097 - 3 - 4 + 062 - 5) ⁵
63472251969 := (6 + 34 - 72 + 251969) ²	:= (-6 - 4 + 097 - 3 + 4 + 062 - 5) ⁵
63664587657 := (63 + 6 - 6 + 4587 - 657) ³	:= (6 + 4 + 097 + 3 + 4 + 06 + 25) ⁵
:= (63 - 6 + 6 + 4587 - 657) ³	:= (6 + 4 + 09 + 73 + 40 + 6 + 2 + 5) ⁵
:= (-6 + 3 + 66 + 4587 - 657) ³	:= (6 + 4 + 09 + 73 - 4 + 062 - 5) ⁵
63904047992 := (-6 + 3904 - 04 + 7 + 99 - 2) ³	:= (6 - 4 + 09 + 73 + 4 + 062 - 5) ⁵
:= (6 - 39 + 04047 - 9 - 9 + 2) ³	:= (6 + 4 - 09 + 73 + 4 + 062 + 5) ⁵
64013554081 := (-64 + 01 + 3 + 554 + 08 + 1) ⁴	:= (64 + 09 + 7 + 34 + 06 + 25) ⁵
:= (-6 - 40 + 1 + 3 + 554 - 08 - 1) ⁴	:= (6 + 40 - 9 + 73 + 4 + 06 + 25) ⁵
:= (-6 - 40 - 1 + 3 + 554 - 08 + 1) ⁴	:= (6 + 40 - 9 + 7 + 34 + 062 + 5) ⁵
:= (-6 - 4 - 013 - 5 + 540 - 8 - 1) ⁴	:= (6 + 4 - 09 + 73 + 40 + 6 + 25) ⁵
:= (-6 - 4 + 01 - 35 + 540 + 8 - 1) ⁴	:= (64 - 09 + 73 - 40 + 62 - 5) ⁵
:= (-6 - 4 - 01 - 35 + 540 + 8 + 1) ⁴	:= (-6 + 40 + 97 - 3 - 40 + 62 - 5) ⁵
:= (640 - 135 - 5 - 4 + 08 - 1) ⁴	:= (-6 - 40 + 97 - 3 + 40 + 62 - 5) ⁵
:= (-64 + 013 + 5 + 540 + 8 + 1) ⁴	:= (6 + 40 + 9 + 73 - 40 + 62 - 5) ⁵
:= (64 - 01 + 355 + 4 + 081) ⁴	:= (6 - 40 + 9 + 73 + 40 + 62 - 5) ⁵
:= (-64 + 01 + 35 + 540 - 8 - 1) ⁴	:= (640 - 9 - 73 - 406 - 2 - 5) ⁵
:= (-64 - 01 + 35 + 540 - 8 + 1) ⁴	:= (6 - 409 - 73 - 4 + 0625) ⁵
:= (6 + 401 + 35 + 54 + 08 - 1) ⁴	:= (640 + 9 - 73 - 406 - 25) ⁵
:= (-6 + 401 - 3 - 5 - 5 + 40 + 81) ⁴	64144108027 := (-64 - 14 + 4108 - 027) ³
:= (-6 - 40 + 13 + 5 + 540 - 8 - 1) ⁴	:= (-6 + 4144 - 108 - 027) ³
:= (-6 + 40 - 1 - 3 + 554 - 081) ⁴	64192192064 := (6 + 4192 - 192 - 06 + 4) ³
:= (6 + 4 - 01 + 35 + 540 - 81) ⁴	:= (-6 + 4192 - 192 + 06 + 4) ³
:= (6 - 40 + 135 - 5 + 408 - 1) ⁴	:= (6 + 4192 - 1 + 9 - 206 + 4) ³
:= (-6 - 40 + 135 + 5 + 408 + 1) ⁴	:= (6 + 4 + 1921 + 9 + 2064) ³
64071253129 := (6 - 4 - 07 - 1 + 253129) ²	64240300125 := (-6 - 4 + 2 + 4030 - 012 - 5) ³
64097340625 := (64 + 097 - 3 - 4 - 06 + 2 - 5) ⁵	64339296875 := (6 + 4 + 33 + 9 + 2 - 9 - 6 + 8 - 7 - 5) ⁷
:= (64 + 09 + 73 - 4 + 06 + 2 - 5) ⁵	:= (6 + 4 + 33 - 9 + 2 + 9 - 6 + 8 - 7 - 5) ⁷
:= (64 - 09 + 73 + 4 + 06 + 2 + 5) ⁵	:= (6 - 4 + 33 + 9 - 2 - 9 + 6 + 8 - 7 - 5) ⁷
:= (6 + 40 + 97 + 3 - 4 + 06 + 2 - 5) ⁵	:= (-6 + 4 + 33 + 9 + 2 - 9 + 6 + 8 - 7 - 5) ⁷
:= (6 + 40 + 97 - 3 - 4 + 06 - 2 + 5) ⁵	:= (6 - 4 + 33 - 9 - 2 + 9 + 6 + 8 - 7 - 5) ⁷
:= (6 + 40 + 97 - 3 + 4 - 06 + 2 + 5) ⁵	:= (-6 + 4 + 33 - 9 + 2 + 9 + 6 + 8 - 7 - 5) ⁷

$$\begin{aligned} & := (-6+4+33+9-2+9-6-8+7-5)^7 & := (64-33+9+2+9-6-8-7+5)^7 \\ & := (6-4+33-9+2-9+6+8+7-5)^7 & := (64-3-39+2+9+6+8-7-5)^7 \\ & := (6-4+33+9-2+9-6-8-7+5)^7 & := (64+3-39-2+9+6-8+7-5)^7 \\ & := (-6+4+33+9+2+9-6-8-7+5)^7 & := (64+3-39+2+9+6-8-7+5)^7 \\ & := (-6-4+33+9-2+9+6-8-7+5)^7 & := (64+3-39-2+9-6+8-7+5)^7 \\ & := (6+4+33-9-2-9+6+8-7+5)^7 & := (64+3-39+2-9-6+8+7+5)^7 \\ & := (6-4+33+9+2-9-6-8+7+5)^7 & := (-64-3-3+92+9-6+8+7-5)^7 \\ & := (6-4+33-9+2+9-6-8+7+5)^7 & := (-64+3-3+92-9+6+8+7-5)^7 \\ & := (-6-4+33+9+2-9+6-8+7+5)^7 & := (-64-3+3+92-9+6+8+7-5)^7 \\ & := (-6-4+33-9+2+9+6-8+7+5)^7 & := (-64+3-3+92+9-6-8+7+5)^7 \\ & := (-6-4+33+9-2-9-6+8+7+5)^7 & := (-64-3+3+92+9-6-8+7+5)^7 \\ & := (-6-4+33-9-2+9-6+8+7+5)^7 & := (-64+3+3+92-9+6-8+7+5)^7 \\ & := (6-4-3+39+2+9+6-8-7-5)^7 & := (-64+3-3+9-2+96+8-7-5)^7 \\ & := (6+4+3+39+2-9-6+8-7-5)^7 & := (-64-3+3+9-2+96+8-7-5)^7 \\ & := (6-4-3+39-2+9-6+8-7-5)^7 & := (-64+3-3-9+2+96+8+7-5)^7 \\ & := (-6+4-3+39+2+9-6+8-7-5)^7 & := (-64-3+3-9+2+96+8+7-5)^7 \\ & := (6-4+3+39-2-9+6+8-7-5)^7 & := (-64+3+3+9-2+96-8-7+5)^7 \\ & := (-6+4+3+39+2-9+6+8-7-5)^7 & := (-64+3+3-9+2+96-8+7+5)^7 \\ & := (-6-4-3+39-2+9+6+8-7-5)^7 & := (-64-3-3-9-2+96+8+7+5)^7 \\ & := (-6+4+3+39-2+9-6-8+7-5)^7 & := (-64+3+3+9+2+9+6-8+75)^7 \\ & := (6+4-3+39-2-9+6-8+7-5)^7 & := (-64+3+3+9-2+9-6+8+75)^7 \\ & := (6-4-3+39+2-9-6+8+7-5)^7 & := (-64-3-3+9-2+9+6+8+75)^7 \\ & := (-6-4-3+39+2-9+6+8+7-5)^7 & := (6+43-39+2+9-6+8+7+5)^7 \\ & := (6-4+3+39-2+9-6-8-7+5)^7 & := (6-43+39-2+9+6+8+7+5)^7 \\ & := (-6+4+3+39+2+9-6-8-7+5)^7 & := (-6+43-39+2+9+6+8+7+5)^7 \\ & := (6+4-3+39+2-9+6-8-7+5)^7 & := (6-43-3+92+9-6-8-7-5)^7 \\ & := (-6-4+3+39-2+9+6-8-7+5)^7 & := (6-43+3+92-9+6-8-7-5)^7 \\ & := (6+4-3+39-2-9-6+8-7+5)^7 & := (-6-43-3+92+9+6-8-7-5)^7 \\ & := (-6+4-3+39-2-9+6+8-7+5)^7 & := (-6-43-3+92-9-6+8+7-5)^7 \\ & := (6-4+3+39+2-9-6-8+7+5)^7 & := (-6-43+3+92-9-6-8+7+5)^7 \\ & := (-6-4-3+39+2+9-6-8+7+5)^7 & := (6-43+3-9+2+96-8-7-5)^7 \\ & := (-6-4+3+39+2-9+6-8+7+5)^7 & := (-6-43-3+9+2+96-8-7-5)^7 \\ & := (-6-4+3+39-2-9-6+8+7+5)^7 & := (-6-43+3-9-2+96+8-7-5)^7 \\ & := (-6-4+3-3-9+2-9-6-8+75)^7 & := (6-43-3-9-2+96-8-7+5)^7 \\ & := (-6-4-3+3-9+2-9-6-8+75)^7 & := (-6-43+3+9+2+9-6-8+75)^7 \\ & := (64-33+9+2-9+6+8-7-5)^7 & := (6-43-3+9+2-9+6-8+75)^7 \\ & := (64-33-9+2+9+6+8-7-5)^7 & := (6-43-3-9+2+9+6-8+75)^7 \\ & := (64-33+9-2+9-6-8+7-5)^7 & := (6-43-3+9-2-9-6+8+75)^7 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} &:= (6-43-3-9-2+9-6+8+75)^7 &:= (6-4-3-3-9-29-6+8+75)^7 \\ &:= (6-43+3-9-2-9+6+8+75)^7 &:= (-6-4+3+3-9-29-6+8+75)^7 \\ &:= (-6-43-3+9-2-9+6+8+75)^7 &:= (-6-4-3-3-9-29+6+8+75)^7 \\ &:= (-6-43-3-9-2+9+6+8+75)^7 &:= (6+4+3-3+9+2+96-87+5)^7 \\ &:= (-6-4+33+9+29-6-8-7-5)^7 &:= (6+4-3+3+9+2+96-87+5)^7 \\ &:= (-6+4+33-9+29-6-8-7+5)^7 &:= (6-4+3+3+9+2+9-68+75)^7 \\ &:= (6+4+33+9-29+6+8-7+5)^7 &:= (64-33-9+29-6-8-7+5)^7 \\ &:= (6+4-33+9+2-9+68-7-5)^7 &:= (-64+33-9-2-9-6+87+5)^7 \\ &:= (6+4-33-9+2+9+68-7-5)^7 &:= (64-3-39+29-6-8-7+5)^7 \\ &:= (-6-4-33+9-2-9+68+7+5)^7 &:= (-64-3+39-2+9+68-7-5)^7 \\ &:= (-6-4-33-9-2+9+68+7+5)^7 &:= (-64-3+39+2-9+68+7-5)^7 \\ &:= (-6-4-33+9+2-9-6+87-5)^7 &:= (64-3+39+2+9+6-87+5)^7 \\ &:= (-6-4-33-9+2+9-6+87-5)^7 &:= (64+3+3-92-9+68-7+5)^7 \\ &:= (6-4-33-9-2-9-6+87+5)^7 &:= (64+3+3+9+29-6+8-75)^7 \\ &:= (-6+4-33-9+2-9-6+87+5)^7 &:= (64-3-3+9+29+6+8-75)^7 \\ &:= (-6-4-33-9-2-9+6+87+5)^7 &:= (-64+3-3+9+29-6-8+75)^7 \\ &:= (-6-4+3+39+29-6-8-7-5)^7 &:= (-64-3+3+9+29-6-8+75)^7 \\ &:= (6+4+3+39-29+6+8-7+5)^7 &:= (-64+3+3-9+29+6-8+75)^7 \\ &:= (6-4-3+39-29+6+8+7+5)^7 &:= (64-3-3-9+2-9+68-75)^7 \\ &:= (6+4-3-39+2+9+68-7-5)^7 &:= (-6+43+39-29-6-8+7-5)^7 \\ &:= (-6-4+3-39+2+9+68+7-5)^7 &:= (6-43+39+29-6+8+7-5)^7 \\ &:= (-6+4+3-39-2+9+68-7+5)^7 &:= (-6-43+39+29+6+8+7-5)^7 \\ &:= (6-4+3-39-2-9+68+7+5)^7 &:= (6+43-39+29+6-8-7+5)^7 \\ &:= (-6+4+3-39+2-9+68+7+5)^7 &:= (-6-43+39-2-9+68-7-5)^7 \\ &:= (-6-4-3-39-2+9+68+7+5)^7 &:= (6+43+3-92+9+68-7+5)^7 \\ &:= (6-4+3-39+2-9-6+87-5)^7 &:= (-6+43+3+92-9-6-87+5)^7 \\ &:= (-6-4-3-39+2+9-6+87-5)^7 &:= (-6-43+3-9+29-6-8+75)^7 \\ &:= (-6-4+3-39+2-9+6+87-5)^7 &:= (6-43+3+9-29+6+8+75)^7 \\ &:= (6-4-3-39-2-9-6+87+5)^7 &:= (6+43-3-9+2-96+87+5)^7 \\ &:= (-6+4-3-39+2-9-6+87+5)^7 &:= (-6+43+3+9+2-9+68-75)^7 \\ &:= (-6-4-3-39-2-9+6+87+5)^7 &:= (-6+43+3-9+2+9+68-75)^7 \\ &:= (6+4-3-3+92+9-68-7+5)^7 &:= (6+4+33+92-96+8-7-5)^7 \\ &:= (-6+4+3+3+92+9-68-7+5)^7 &:= (6-4+33-92+96+8-7-5)^7 \\ &:= (6-4+3+3+92-9-68+7+5)^7 &:= (6-4+33+92-96-8+7+5)^7 \\ &:= (-6-4+3-3+92+9-68+7+5)^7 &:= (-6-4+33+92+9-6-8-75)^7 \\ &:= (-6-4-3+3+92+9-68+7+5)^7 &:= (6-4-33+9-29-6+87+5)^7 \\ &:= (6+4+3-3+92+9+6-87+5)^7 &:= (-6-4-33+9-29+6+87+5)^7 \\ &:= (6+4-3+3+92+9+6-87+5)^7 &:= (6-4+3-39-29+6+87+5)^7 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} &:= (6 + 4 - 3 + 39 + 2 - 96 + 8 + 75)^7 \\ &:= (6 + 4 - 3 - 3 + 9 + 29 + 68 - 75)^7 \\ &:= (-6 + 4 + 3 + 3 + 9 + 29 + 68 - 75)^7 \\ &:= (6 - 4 + 3 + 3 - 9 + 29 - 68 + 75)^7 \\ &:= (-6 - 4 + 3 - 3 + 9 + 29 - 68 + 75)^7 \\ &:= (-6 - 4 - 3 + 3 + 9 + 29 - 68 + 75)^7 \\ &:= (-64 + 33 + 9 - 29 - 6 + 87 + 5)^7 \\ &:= (-64 + 3 + 39 - 29 - 6 + 87 + 5)^7 \\ &:= (-64 - 3 - 3 + 92 + 96 - 8 - 75)^7 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} &:= (-64 - 3 - 3 - 9 - 29 + 68 + 75)^7 \\ &:= (-6 + 43 + 39 + 29 - 68 - 7 + 5)^7 \\ &:= (-6 + 43 - 39 - 29 + 68 - 7 + 5)^7 \\ &:= (-6 - 43 - 3 - 92 + 96 + 8 + 75)^7 \\ &:= (-6 + 4 + 339 - 296 - 8 + 7 - 5)^7 \\ &:= (6 - 4 + 339 - 296 - 8 - 7 + 5)^7 \\ &:= (-6 - 4 - 33 + 92 - 96 + 87 - 5)^7 \end{aligned}$$

$$\mathbf{64432972729} := (-64 + 4329 + 7 - 272 + 9)^3$$

$$:= (-6 - 4 + 52 + 412 - 8 + 2 + 56)^4$$

$$\mathbf{64524128256} := (6 - 4 + 524 + 1 - 2 - 8 - 2 - 5 - 6)^4$$

$$:= (6 - 4 - 5 + 241 + 2 + 8 + 256)^4$$

$$:= (-6 + 4 + 524 + 1 + 2 - 8 - 2 - 5 - 6)^4$$

$$:= (645 + 2 + 4 - 128 - 25 + 6)^4$$

$$:= (-6 + 4 + 524 + 1 - 2 - 8 + 2 - 5 - 6)^4$$

$$:= (64 + 52 + 4 + 128 + 256)^4$$

$$:= (-6 - 4 + 524 - 1 + 2 - 8 - 2 + 5 - 6)^4$$

$$\mathbf{64674354744} := (6 - 4 + 6 - 743 + 5 + 4744)^3$$

$$:= (-64 - 674 + 3 + 5 + 4744)^3$$

$$:= (-6 - 4 + 524 - 1 - 2 - 8 + 2 + 5 - 6)^4$$

$$\mathbf{64722703375} := (647 + 2 - 2 - 7 + 03375)^3$$

$$:= (647 - 2 + 2 - 7 + 03375)^3$$

$$:= (-6 - 4 + 524 + 1 - 2 - 8 - 2 - 5 + 6)^4$$

$$\mathbf{65037750625} := (6 + 503 + 7 + 7 - 5 - 06 - 2 - 5)^4$$

$$:= (-6 + 503 + 7 + 7 - 5 + 06 - 2 - 5)^4$$

$$:= (6 + 452 + 41 - 2 + 8 - 2 - 5 + 6)^4$$

$$:= (6 + 503 + 7 - 7 + 5 - 06 + 2 - 5)^4$$

$$:= (6 + 452 + 4 + 1 + 28 + 2 + 5 + 6)^4$$

$$:= (6 + 503 - 7 + 7 + 5 - 06 + 2 - 5)^4$$

$$:= (6 + 452 + 4 + 1 + 2 + 8 + 25 + 6)^4$$

$$:= (-6 + 503 + 7 - 7 + 5 + 06 + 2 - 5)^4$$

$$:= (6 + 4 + 524 + 1 - 28 - 2 + 5 - 6)^4$$

$$:= (-6 + 503 - 7 + 7 + 5 + 06 + 2 - 5)^4$$

$$:= (6 + 4 + 524 - 1 - 28 - 2 - 5 + 6)^4$$

$$:= (6 + 503 + 7 - 7 - 5 - 06 + 2 + 5)^4$$

$$:= (-6 + 4 + 524 + 1 - 28 - 2 + 5 + 6)^4$$

$$:= (6 + 503 - 7 + 7 - 5 - 06 + 2 + 5)^4$$

$$:= (6 - 4 + 524 - 1 + 2 + 8 - 25 - 6)^4$$

$$:= (-6 + 503 + 7 - 7 - 5 + 06 + 2 + 5)^4$$

$$:= (6 + 4 + 524 - 1 - 2 - 8 - 25 + 6)^4$$

$$:= (-6 + 503 - 7 + 7 - 5 + 06 + 2 + 5)^4$$

$$:= (-6 - 4 + 524 - 1 + 2 + 8 - 25 + 6)^4$$

$$:= (-6 - 5 + 03 + 7 + 7 + 506 - 2 - 5)^4$$

$$:= (6 - 4 + 5 + 2 + 412 + 82 - 5 + 6)^4$$

$$:= (-6 + 5 + 03 + 7 - 7 + 506 + 2 - 5)^4$$

$$:= (6 - 4 - 5 + 2 + 412 + 82 + 5 + 6)^4$$

$$:= (-6 + 5 + 03 - 7 + 7 + 506 + 2 - 5)^4$$

$$:= (645 + 2 - 4 + 1 - 2 - 82 - 56)^4$$

$$:= (-6 + 5 - 03 + 7 - 7 + 506 - 2 + 5)^4$$

$$:= (645 - 2 - 4 + 1 + 2 - 82 - 56)^4$$

$$:= (-6 + 5 - 03 - 7 + 7 + 506 - 2 + 5)^4$$

$$:= (64 + 524 + 1 - 2 - 82 + 5 - 6)^4$$

$$:= (-6 + 5 - 03 - 7 + 7 + 506 + 2 + 5)^4$$

$$:= (64 + 524 - 1 - 2 - 82 - 5 + 6)^4$$

$$:= (-6 - 5 + 03 - 7 + 7 + 506 + 2 + 5)^4$$

$$:= (6 + 452 - 4 - 12 + 8 - 2 + 56)^4$$

$$:= (65 + 0377 + 50 + 6 + 2 + 5)^4$$

$$:= (-6 + 452 - 4 + 12 - 8 + 2 + 56)^4$$

$$:= (6 + 50 + 377 + 5 + 062 + 5)^4$$

$$:= (-6 + 452 + 4 - 12 + 8 + 2 + 56)^4$$

$$:= (6 + 5 + 0377 + 50 + 62 + 5)^4$$

$$:= (6 + 45 + 2 + 412 + 8 + 25 + 6)^4$$

$$:= (-6 - 4 + 524 - 1 - 28 + 25 - 6)^4$$

$$\begin{aligned} &:= (6 + 503 + 77 - 50 - 6 - 25)^4 \\ &:= (-6 + 503 + 77 - 50 + 6 - 25)^4 \\ &:= (-6 - 50 + 37 - 7 + 506 + 25)^4 \\ &:= (-6 - 50 + 3 + 77 + 506 - 25)^4 \\ \mathbf{65402116389} &:= (6 + 5 + 4021 + 1 - 6 + 3 + 8 - 9)^3 \\ &:= (6 - 5 + 4021 - 1 + 6 + 3 + 8 - 9)^3 \\ &:= (-6 + 5 + 4021 + 1 + 6 + 3 + 8 - 9)^3 \\ &:= (6 + 5 + 4021 - 1 - 6 + 3 - 8 + 9)^3 \\ &:= (-6 + 5 + 4021 - 1 + 6 + 3 - 8 + 9)^3 \\ &:= (6 - 5 + 4021 - 1 - 6 - 3 + 8 + 9)^3 \\ &:= (-6 + 5 + 4021 + 1 - 6 - 3 + 8 + 9)^3 \\ &:= (-6 - 5 + 4021 - 1 + 6 - 3 + 8 + 9)^3 \\ \mathbf{65554433296} &:= (-65 + 554 + 4 + 3 - 3 - 2 + 9 + 6)^4 \\ &:= (-65 + 554 + 4 - 3 + 3 - 2 + 9 + 6)^4 \\ &:= (65 + 5 - 5 + 443 - 3 - 2 + 9 - 6)^4 \\ &:= (65 - 5 + 5 + 443 - 3 - 2 + 9 - 6)^4 \\ &:= (65 - 5 - 5 + 443 + 3 + 2 + 9 - 6)^4 \\ &:= (65 + 5 - 5 + 443 + 3 - 2 - 9 + 6)^4 \\ &:= (65 - 5 + 5 + 443 + 3 - 2 - 9 + 6)^4 \\ &:= (6 + 555 - 44 + 3 + 3 - 2 - 9 - 6)^4 \\ &:= (-6 + 555 - 44 + 3 - 3 - 2 + 9 - 6)^4 \\ &:= (-6 + 555 - 44 - 3 + 3 - 2 + 9 - 6)^4 \\ &:= (6 + 555 - 44 - 3 - 3 - 2 - 9 + 6)^4 \\ &:= (-6 + 555 - 44 + 3 + 3 - 2 - 9 + 6)^4 \\ &:= (6 + 555 + 4 - 43 - 3 + 2 - 9 - 6)^4 \\ &:= (-6 + 555 - 4 - 43 + 3 - 2 + 9 - 6)^4 \\ &:= (6 + 555 - 4 - 43 - 3 - 2 - 9 + 6)^4 \\ &:= (-6 + 555 + 4 - 43 - 3 + 2 - 9 + 6)^4 \\ &:= (-6 + 555 - 4 - 4 + 3 - 3 - 29 - 6)^4 \\ &:= (-6 + 555 - 4 - 4 - 3 + 3 - 29 - 6)^4 \\ &:= (6 - 55 + 544 + 3 + 3 + 2 + 9 - 6)^4 \\ &:= (6 - 55 + 544 - 3 - 3 + 2 + 9 + 6)^4 \\ &:= (-6 - 55 + 544 + 3 + 3 + 2 + 9 + 6)^4 \\ &:= (6 + 55 - 5 + 4 + 433 - 2 + 9 + 6)^4 \\ &:= (6 + 5 + 554 - 43 - 3 + 2 - 9 - 6)^4 \\ &:= (-6 + 5 + 554 - 43 - 3 + 2 - 9 + 6)^4 \\ &:= (-6 - 5 + 554 + 4 - 3 - 3 - 29 - 6)^4 \\ &:= (6 - 5 + 55 + 4 + 433 - 2 + 9 + 6)^4 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} &:= (-6 + 5 - 5 + 544 - 33 - 2 + 9 - 6)^4 \\ &:= (-6 - 5 + 5 + 544 - 33 - 2 + 9 - 6)^4 \\ &:= (6 - 5 - 5 + 544 - 33 + 2 - 9 + 6)^4 \\ &:= (6 + 5 - 5 + 544 + 3 - 32 - 9 - 6)^4 \\ &:= (6 - 5 + 5 + 544 + 3 - 32 - 9 - 6)^4 \\ &:= (-6 + 5 - 5 + 544 - 3 - 32 + 9 - 6)^4 \\ &:= (-6 - 5 + 5 + 544 - 3 - 32 + 9 - 6)^4 \\ &:= (-6 + 5 - 5 + 544 + 3 - 32 - 9 + 6)^4 \\ &:= (-6 - 5 + 5 + 544 + 3 - 32 - 9 + 6)^4 \\ &:= (6 + 5 - 5 + 54 + 433 - 2 + 9 + 6)^4 \\ &:= (6 - 5 + 5 + 54 + 433 - 2 + 9 + 6)^4 \\ &:= (-6 - 5 - 5 - 5 - 4 + 433 + 2 + 96)^4 \\ &:= (655 - 5 - 44 - 3 - 3 + 2 - 96)^4 \\ &:= (655 - 5 - 4 - 43 - 3 + 2 - 96)^4 \\ &:= (-65 - 5 + 544 + 33 + 2 - 9 + 6)^4 \\ &:= (-65 - 5 + 544 - 3 + 32 + 9 - 6)^4 \\ &:= (-65 - 5 + 544 + 3 + 32 - 9 + 6)^4 \\ &:= (65 - 5 + 544 + 3 - 3 - 2 - 96)^4 \\ &:= (65 - 5 + 544 - 3 + 3 - 2 - 96)^4 \\ &:= (-6 - 55 + 544 + 3 - 3 + 29 - 6)^4 \\ &:= (-6 - 55 + 544 - 3 + 3 + 29 - 6)^4 \\ &:= (-6 + 55 + 5 - 4 + 433 + 29 - 6)^4 \\ &:= (-6 + 5 + 55 - 4 + 433 + 29 - 6)^4 \\ &:= (6 - 5 - 5 + 54 + 433 + 29 - 6)^4 \\ &:= (-6 - 5 - 5 + 54 + 433 + 29 + 6)^4 \\ &:= (-6 + 5 + 5 - 5 + 443 - 32 + 96)^4 \\ &:= (-6 + 5 - 5 + 5 + 443 - 32 + 96)^4 \\ &:= (-6 - 5 + 5 + 5 + 443 - 32 + 96)^4 \\ &:= (-65 + 554 + 43 - 3 - 29 + 6)^4 \\ &:= (-65 + 5 - 5 + 443 + 32 + 96)^4 \\ &:= (-65 - 5 + 5 + 443 + 32 + 96)^4 \\ &:= (655 - 5 - 443 + 3 + 296)^4 \\ \mathbf{65597103937} &:= (6 + 5 + 5 + 9 + 71 + 03937)^3 \\ &:= (65 + 5 + 9 + 7 + 10 + 3937)^3 \\ \mathbf{65841382872} &:= (-6 + 5 - 8 + 4138 - 2 - 87 - 2)^3 \\ \mathbf{65939264000} &:= (6 + 5 + 9 + 3 + 9 + 2 + 6 + 4000)^3 \\ &:= (65 - 9 - 3 - 9 + 2 - 6 + 4000)^3 \\ &:= (6 + 5 + 9 + 3 - 9 + 26 + 4000)^3 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 &:= (-6 + 5 + 9 - 3 + 9 + 26 + 4000)^3 \\
 &:= (6 + 5 - 9 + 3 + 9 + 26 + 4000)^3 \\
 &:= (65 + 9 + 3926 + 40 + 00)^3 \\
 &:= (-6 + 59 - 39 + 26 + 4000)^3 \\
 \mathbf{66074188401} &:= (-6 + 607 - 4 + 1 - 88 - 4 + 01)^4 \\
 &:= (-6 + 607 - 4 + 1 - 8 - 84 + 01)^4 \\
 &:= (66 - 07 - 41 + 88 + 401)^4 \\
 &:= (6 + 60 - 7 - 41 + 88 + 401)^4 \\
 &:= (660 + 74 - 188 - 40 + 1)^4 \\
 \mathbf{66233489336} &:= (662 + 3348 + 9 + 33 - 6)^3 \\
 \mathbf{66338290976} &:= (66 + 3 + 3 + 8 - 2 + 90 - 9 - 7 - 6)^5 \\
 &:= (66 + 3 - 3 - 8 + 2 + 90 + 9 - 7 - 6)^5 \\
 &:= (66 - 3 + 3 - 8 + 2 + 90 + 9 - 7 - 6)^5 \\
 &:= (66 - 3 - 3 + 8 - 2 + 90 - 9 - 7 + 6)^5 \\
 &:= (66 + 3 + 3 - 8 + 2 + 90 - 9 - 7 + 6)^5 \\
 &:= (66 - 3 - 3 + 8 + 2 + 9 - 09 + 76)^5 \\
 &:= (66 - 3 - 3 + 8 + 2 - 9 + 09 + 76)^5 \\
 &:= (6 + 63 + 3 + 8 - 2 + 90 - 9 - 7 - 6)^5 \\
 &:= (-6 + 63 - 3 + 8 - 2 + 90 + 9 - 7 - 6)^5 \\
 &:= (6 + 63 - 3 - 8 + 2 + 90 + 9 - 7 - 6)^5 \\
 &:= (-6 + 63 - 3 + 8 + 2 + 90 - 9 + 7 - 6)^5 \\
 &:= (-6 + 63 + 3 + 8 - 2 + 90 - 9 - 7 + 6)^5 \\
 &:= (-6 + 63 + 3 + 8 + 2 - 9 + 09 + 76)^5 \\
 &:= (-6 + 63 + 3 + 8 + 2 - 9 + 09 + 76)^5 \\
 &:= (6 + 6 + 33 + 82 + 9 + 09 + 7 - 6)^5 \\
 &:= (6 - 6 + 33 + 82 + 9 + 09 + 7 + 6)^5 \\
 &:= (-6 + 6 + 33 + 82 + 9 + 09 + 7 + 6)^5 \\
 &:= (-6 - 6 - 3 - 3 + 82 + 90 - 9 + 7 - 6)^5 \\
 &:= (-6 - 6 - 3 - 3 + 82 - 9 + 097 - 6)^5 \\
 &:= (6 + 6 - 3 - 3 + 82 - 9 - 09 + 76)^5 \\
 &:= (6 - 6 + 3 + 3 + 82 - 9 - 09 + 76)^5 \\
 &:= (-6 + 6 + 3 + 3 + 82 - 9 - 09 + 76)^5 \\
 &:= (-6 - 6 + 3 - 3 + 82 + 9 - 09 + 76)^5 \\
 &:= (-6 - 6 - 3 + 3 + 82 + 9 - 09 + 76)^5 \\
 &:= (-6 - 6 + 3 - 3 + 82 - 9 + 09 + 76)^5
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 &:= (-6 - 6 - 3 + 3 + 82 - 9 + 09 + 76)^5 \\
 &:= (6 + 6 + 3 + 3 + 8 + 29 + 097 - 6)^5 \\
 &:= (6 + 6 - 3 - 3 + 8 + 29 + 097 + 6)^5 \\
 &:= (6 - 6 + 3 + 3 + 8 + 29 + 097 + 6)^5 \\
 &:= (-6 + 6 + 3 + 3 + 8 + 29 + 097 + 6)^5 \\
 &:= (66 - 33 + 82 + 9 + 09 + 7 + 6)^5 \\
 &:= (66 + 33 + 8 + 29 + 09 + 7 - 6)^5 \\
 &:= (66 + 3 + 38 + 29 + 09 + 7 - 6)^5 \\
 &:= (6 + 63 + 38 + 29 + 09 + 7 - 6)^5 \\
 &:= (-6 + 63 + 38 + 29 + 09 + 7 + 6)^5 \\
 &:= (-6 - 6 - 33 + 8 + 2 + 90 + 97 - 6)^5 \\
 &:= (6 + 6 - 33 + 8 + 2 + 90 - 9 + 76)^5 \\
 &:= (-66 - 3 + 38 + 2 + 90 + 9 + 76)^5 \\
 &:= (-6 - 63 + 38 + 2 + 90 + 9 + 76)^5 \\
 &:= (6 - 6 - 33 - 8 + 290 - 97 - 6)^5 \\
 &:= (-6 + 6 - 33 - 8 + 290 - 97 - 6)^5 \\
 &:= (-6 - 6 - 33 - 8 + 290 - 97 + 6)^5 \\
 &:= (6 - 6 - 3 - 38 + 290 - 97 - 6)^5 \\
 &:= (-6 + 6 - 3 - 38 + 290 - 97 - 6)^5 \\
 &:= (-6 - 6 - 3 - 38 + 290 - 97 + 6)^5 \\
 &:= (-66 + 33 - 8 + 290 - 97 - 6)^5 \\
 \mathbf{66597028096} &:= (-6 + 659 - 70 + 2 - 80 + 9 - 6)^4 \\
 &:= (66 + 59 + 7 + 0280 + 96)^4 \\
 &:= (66 + 5 - 9 + 70 + 280 + 96)^4 \\
 &:= (6 + 65 - 9 + 70 + 280 + 96)^4 \\
 &:= (665 - 970 - 2 + 809 + 6)^4 \\
 \mathbf{66676466375} &:= (66 - 676 + 4663 + 7 - 5)^3 \\
 \mathbf{66824563112} &:= (66 + 824 + 56 + 3112)^3 \\
 \mathbf{66873977379} &:= (66 + 8 + 7 + 3977 + 3 + 7 - 9)^3 \\
 &:= (6 + 68 + 7 + 3977 + 3 + 7 - 9)^3 \\
 &:= (-6 + 68 + 7 + 3977 - 3 + 7 + 9)^3 \\
 &:= (6 - 6 + 87 + 3977 - 3 + 7 - 9)^3 \\
 &:= (-6 + 6 + 87 + 3977 - 3 + 7 - 9)^3 \\
 \mathbf{67121414144} &:= (-67 + 1 - 2 - 1 + 4141 - 4 - 4)^3 \\
 &:= (-67 - 1 - 2 + 1 + 4141 - 4 - 4)^3 \\
 &:= (6 - 71 - 2 - 14 + 1 + 4144)^3 \\
 &:= (-6 - 7 + 1 - 21 + 4141 - 44)^3 \\
 \mathbf{67122964561} &:= (-6 + 71 + 2 + 2 - 9 - 6 + 456 - 1)^4
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 &:= (671 + 2 + 2 - 96 - 4 - 5 - 61)^4 \\
 &:= (671 - 2 - 2 - 96 + 4 - 5 - 61)^4 \\
 &:= (67 - 12 + 2 - 9 + 6 + 456 - 1)^4 \\
 &:= (-67 + 12 + 2 - 9 + 6 + 4 + 561)^4 \\
 &:= (-67 + 1 + 2 - 2 - 9 + 645 - 61)^4 \\
 &:= (-67 + 1 - 2 + 2 - 9 + 645 - 61)^4 \\
 &:= (6 + 71 - 22 - 9 + 6 + 456 + 1)^4 \\
 &:= (6 + 71 - 2 - 29 + 6 + 456 + 1)^4 \\
 &:= (-6 - 71 - 2 + 29 - 6 + 4 + 561)^4 \\
 &:= (6 - 7 - 12 - 29 - 6 - 4 + 561)^4 \\
 &:= (-6 - 7 - 12 - 29 + 6 - 4 + 561)^4 \\
 &:= (6 + 7 - 12 + 2 + 9 - 64 + 561)^4 \\
 &:= (671 - 229 + 6 + 4 + 56 + 1)^4 \\
 &:= (-67 + 122 - 9 + 6 + 456 + 1)^4 \\
 &:= (-67 - 12 + 29 - 6 + 4 + 561)^4 \\
 &:= (-67 + 1 + 22 + 96 + 456 + 1)^4 \\
 \mathbf{67259310336} &:= (-6 + 7 + 259310 - 3 + 36)^2 \\
 &:= (67 + 259310 + 3 - 36)^2 \\
 \mathbf{67817482552} &:= (67 - 817 + 4825 + 5 - 2)^3 \\
 &:= (-678 - 17 + 4825 - 52)^3 \\
 \mathbf{67917312000} &:= (-6 - 7917 + 3 + 12000)^3 \\
 \mathbf{67967263441} &:= (679 - 6 - 7 - 26 + 3441)^3 \\
 &:= (6796 + 726 - 3441)^3 \\
 \mathbf{68167314125} &:= (6 + 8 - 16 - 7 - 31 + 4125)^3 \\
 \mathbf{68184176641} &:= (68 + 1 + 8 + 417 + 6 + 6 + 4 + 1)^4 \\
 &:= (6 + 81 - 8 + 417 + 6 + 6 + 4 - 1)^4 \\
 &:= (6 + 8 + 1 + 8 + 417 + 66 + 4 + 1)^4 \\
 &:= (6 + 8 + 1 + 8 + 417 + 6 + 64 + 1)^4 \\
 &:= (681 - 84 + 1 - 76 - 6 - 4 - 1)^4 \\
 &:= (681 - 84 - 1 - 76 - 6 - 4 + 1)^4 \\
 &:= (-68 + 1 + 8 + 4 + 1 - 76 + 641)^4 \\
 &:= (681 - 84 - 17 - 66 - 4 + 1)^4 \\
 &:= (681 - 84 - 17 - 6 - 64 + 1)^4 \\
 &:= (68 - 184 - 1 - 7 - 6 + 641)^4 \\
 &:= (-68 - 1 - 84 + 17 + 6 + 641)^4 \\
 &:= (-6 - 81 - 84 + 17 + 664 + 1)^4 \\
 &:= (-6 - 81 - 8 + 41 - 76 + 641)^4 \\
 &:= (68 - 18 - 4 - 176 + 641)^4
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 \mathbf{68641485507} &:= (6 + 86 + 4 - 1 - 4 + 8 + 55 - 07)^5 \\
 &:= (6 + 86 - 4 - 1 + 4 + 8 + 55 - 07)^5 \\
 &:= (6 + 86 + 4 + 1 - 4 - 8 + 55 + 07)^5 \\
 &:= (6 + 86 - 4 + 1 + 4 - 8 + 55 + 07)^5 \\
 &:= (6 + 86 + 4 + 1 + 4 + 8 - 5 + 50 - 7)^5 \\
 &:= (6 + 86 + 4 - 1 - 4 + 8 + 5 + 50 - 7)^5 \\
 &:= (6 + 86 - 4 - 1 + 4 + 8 + 5 + 50 - 7)^5 \\
 &:= (-6 + 86 + 4 - 1 + 4 + 8 - 5 + 50 + 7)^5 \\
 &:= (6 + 86 + 4 + 1 - 4 - 8 + 5 + 50 + 7)^5 \\
 &:= (6 + 86 - 4 + 1 + 4 - 8 + 5 + 50 + 7)^5 \\
 &:= (6 + 8 + 6 - 4 + 148 - 5 - 5 - 07)^5 \\
 &:= (6 - 8 - 6 + 4 + 148 + 5 + 5 - 07)^5 \\
 &:= (-6 - 8 + 6 + 4 + 148 + 5 + 5 - 07)^5 \\
 &:= (-6 + 8 - 6 - 4 + 148 + 5 - 5 + 07)^5 \\
 &:= (-6 + 8 - 6 - 4 + 148 - 5 + 5 + 07)^5 \\
 &:= (6 + 8 + 6 + 4 - 1 - 4 + 85 + 50 - 7)^5 \\
 &:= (6 + 8 + 6 - 4 - 1 + 4 + 85 + 50 - 7)^5 \\
 &:= (6 - 8 + 6 + 4 + 1 - 4 + 85 + 50 + 7)^5 \\
 &:= (6 - 8 + 6 - 4 + 1 + 4 + 85 + 50 + 7)^5 \\
 &:= (-6 + 8 - 6 + 4 + 1 + 4 + 85 + 50 + 7)^5 \\
 &:= (68 + 64 + 14 + 8 + 5 - 5 - 07)^5 \\
 &:= (68 + 64 + 14 + 8 - 5 + 5 - 07)^5 \\
 &:= (68 - 6 + 41 + 4 - 8 + 55 - 07)^5 \\
 &:= (68 - 6 + 41 + 4 - 8 + 5 + 50 - 7)^5 \\
 &:= (68 + 6 + 4 - 14 + 85 + 5 - 07)^5 \\
 &:= (-6 + 86 + 41 - 4 - 8 - 5 + 50 - 7)^5 \\
 &:= (6 + 86 - 4 - 14 + 85 - 5 - 07)^5 \\
 &:= (6 + 8 + 64 - 14 + 85 + 5 - 07)^5 \\
 &:= (-6 - 8 + 64 + 14 + 85 + 5 - 07)^5 \\
 &:= (-6 - 8 + 64 + 1 + 48 + 55 - 07)^5 \\
 &:= (6 - 8 + 64 - 1 + 48 - 5 + 50 - 7)^5 \\
 &:= (-6 - 8 + 64 + 1 + 48 + 5 + 50 - 7)^5 \\
 &:= (-6 + 8 - 6 + 41 + 48 + 55 + 07)^5 \\
 &:= (6 + 8 + 6 + 41 + 48 - 5 + 50 - 7)^5 \\
 &:= (-6 + 8 - 6 + 41 + 48 + 5 + 50 + 7)^5 \\
 &:= (-68 + 64 + 148 + 5 + 5 - 07)^5 \\
 &:= (68 + 64 + 1 - 48 + 55 + 07)^5 \\
 &:= (68 + 64 + 1 - 48 + 5 + 50 + 7)^5
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} & := (68 + 6 + 41 + 4 + 85 - 50 - 7)^5 & := (6 + 8 + 7 + 1 - 9 - 4 + 7 - 6 + 7 - 3 - 6)^{12} \\ & := (6 + 86 - 41 + 48 + 55 - 07)^5 & := (6 - 8 + 7 - 1 + 9 - 4 + 7 - 6 + 7 - 3 - 6)^{12} \\ & := (6 + 86 + 41 - 48 + 55 + 07)^5 & := (-6 + 8 + 7 - 1 - 9 + 4 + 7 - 6 + 7 - 3 - 6)^{36} \\ & := (6 + 86 - 41 + 48 + 5 + 50 - 7)^5 & := (6 + 8 - 7 + 1 - 9 + 4 + 7 - 6 + 7 - 3 - 6)^{36} \\ & := (6 + 86 + 41 - 48 + 5 + 50 + 7)^5 & := (-6 + 8 + 7 + 1 - 9 + 4 + 7 - 6 + 7 - 3 - 6)^{18} \\ & := (6 + 8 + 641 - 4 + 8 - 5 - 507)^5 & := (6 + 8 + 7 + 1 - 9 + 4 + 7 - 6 + 7 - 3 - 6)^9 \\ & := (-6 + 8 - 6 - 414 + 8 + 550 + 7)^5 & := (6 - 8 - 7 - 1 + 9 + 4 + 7 - 6 + 7 - 3 - 6)^{36} \\ & := (686 - 41 - 4 + 8 + 5 - 507)^5 & := (-6 - 8 + 7 - 1 + 9 + 4 + 7 - 6 + 7 - 3 - 6)^{18} \\ & := (686 - 4 + 14 + 8 - 550 - 7)^5 & := (6 - 8 + 7 - 1 + 9 + 4 + 7 - 6 + 7 - 3 - 6)^9 \\ & := (686 + 4 - 1 - 485 - 50 - 7)^5 & := (6 - 8 - 7 + 1 + 9 + 4 + 7 - 6 + 7 - 3 - 6)^{18} \\ & := (-68 + 641 - 4 + 85 - 507)^5 & := (-6 + 8 - 7 + 1 + 9 + 4 + 7 - 6 + 7 - 3 - 6)^{12} \\ \mathbf{68719476736} & := (6 + 8 + 7 - 1 + 9 + 4 - 7 - 6 - 7 - 3 - 6)^{18} & := (6 + 8 + 7 - 1 - 9 - 4 - 7 + 6 + 7 - 3 - 6)^{18} \\ & := (6 + 8 + 7 + 1 - 9 + 4 + 7 - 6 - 7 - 3 - 6)^{36} & := (6 + 8 - 7 - 1 + 9 - 4 - 7 + 6 + 7 - 3 - 6)^{12} \\ & := (6 + 8 - 7 - 1 + 9 + 4 + 7 - 6 - 7 - 3 - 6)^{18} & := (6 - 8 + 7 + 1 + 9 - 4 - 7 + 6 + 7 - 3 - 6)^{12} \\ & := (6 - 8 + 7 - 1 + 9 + 4 + 7 - 6 - 7 - 3 - 6)^{36} & := (-6 + 8 + 7 + 1 - 9 + 4 - 7 + 6 + 7 - 3 - 6)^{36} \\ & := (6 - 8 + 7 + 1 + 9 + 4 + 7 - 6 - 7 - 3 - 6)^{18} & := (-6 + 8 - 7 - 1 + 9 + 4 - 7 + 6 + 7 - 3 - 6)^{18} \\ & := (-6 + 8 + 7 + 1 + 9 + 4 + 7 - 6 - 7 - 3 - 6)^{12} & := (6 + 8 - 7 - 1 + 9 + 4 - 7 + 6 + 7 - 3 - 6)^9 \\ & := (6 + 8 + 7 - 1 + 9 - 4 - 7 + 6 - 7 - 3 - 6)^{12} & := (-6 - 8 + 7 - 1 + 9 + 4 - 7 + 6 + 7 - 3 - 6)^{36} \\ & := (6 + 8 - 7 - 1 + 9 + 4 - 7 + 6 - 7 - 3 - 6)^{36} & := (6 - 8 - 7 + 1 + 9 + 4 - 7 + 6 + 7 - 3 - 6)^{36} \\ & := (-6 + 8 + 7 - 1 + 9 + 4 - 7 + 6 - 7 - 3 - 6)^{18} & := (-6 - 8 + 7 + 1 + 9 + 4 - 7 + 6 + 7 - 3 - 6)^{18} \\ & := (6 + 8 + 7 - 1 + 9 + 4 - 7 + 6 - 7 - 3 - 6)^9 & := (6 - 8 + 7 + 1 + 9 + 4 - 7 + 6 + 7 - 3 - 6)^9 \\ & := (6 + 8 - 7 + 1 + 9 + 4 - 7 + 6 - 7 - 3 - 6)^{18} & := (6 + 8 - 7 - 1 - 9 - 4 + 7 + 6 + 7 - 3 - 6)^{18} \\ & := (6 - 8 + 7 + 1 + 9 + 4 - 7 + 6 - 7 - 3 - 6)^{36} & := (6 - 8 + 7 - 1 - 9 - 4 + 7 + 6 + 7 - 3 - 6)^{36} \\ & := (6 + 8 + 7 - 1 - 9 - 4 + 7 + 6 - 7 - 3 - 6)^{18} & := (6 - 8 + 7 + 1 - 9 - 4 + 7 + 6 + 7 - 3 - 6)^{18} \\ & := (6 + 8 - 7 - 1 + 9 - 4 + 7 + 6 - 7 - 3 - 6)^{12} & := (-6 + 8 + 7 + 1 - 9 - 4 + 7 + 6 + 7 - 3 - 6)^{12} \\ & := (6 - 8 + 7 + 1 + 9 - 4 + 7 + 6 - 7 - 3 - 6)^{12} & := (-6 - 8 + 7 - 1 + 9 - 4 + 7 + 6 + 7 - 3 - 6)^{12} \\ & := (-6 + 8 + 7 + 1 - 9 + 4 + 7 + 6 - 7 - 3 - 6)^{36} & := (6 - 8 - 7 + 1 + 9 - 4 + 7 + 6 + 7 - 3 - 6)^{12} \\ & := (-6 + 8 - 7 - 1 + 9 + 4 + 7 + 6 - 7 - 3 - 6)^{18} & := (-6 + 8 - 7 + 1 - 9 + 4 + 7 + 6 + 7 - 3 - 6)^{36} \\ & := (6 + 8 - 7 - 1 + 9 + 4 + 7 + 6 - 7 - 3 - 6)^9 & := (-6 + 8 + 7 + 1 - 9 + 4 + 7 + 6 + 7 - 3 - 6)^9 \\ & := (-6 - 8 + 7 - 1 + 9 + 4 + 7 + 6 - 7 - 3 - 6)^{36} & := (-6 - 8 - 7 - 1 + 9 + 4 + 7 + 6 + 7 - 3 - 6)^{36} \\ & := (6 - 8 - 7 + 1 + 9 + 4 + 7 + 6 - 7 - 3 - 6)^{36} & := (-6 - 8 + 7 - 1 + 9 + 4 + 7 + 6 + 7 - 3 - 6)^9 \\ & := (-6 - 8 + 7 + 1 + 9 + 4 + 7 + 6 - 7 - 3 - 6)^{18} & := (-6 - 8 - 7 + 1 + 9 + 4 + 7 + 6 + 7 - 3 - 6)^{18} \\ & := (6 - 8 + 7 + 1 + 9 + 4 + 7 + 6 - 7 - 3 - 6)^9 & := (6 - 8 - 7 + 1 + 9 + 4 + 7 + 6 + 7 - 3 - 6)^9 \\ & := (6 + 8 + 7 + 1 - 9 + 4 - 7 - 6 + 7 - 3 - 6)^{36} & := (6 + 8 + 7 - 1 + 9 - 4 - 7 - 6 - 7 + 3 - 6)^{36} \\ & := (6 + 8 - 7 - 1 + 9 + 4 - 7 - 6 + 7 - 3 - 6)^{18} & := (6 + 8 + 7 + 1 + 9 - 4 - 7 - 6 - 7 + 3 - 6)^{18} \\ & := (6 - 8 + 7 - 1 + 9 + 4 - 7 - 6 + 7 - 3 - 6)^{36} & := (6 + 8 - 7 - 1 + 9 - 4 + 7 - 6 - 7 + 3 - 6)^{36} \\ & := (6 - 8 + 7 + 1 + 9 + 4 - 7 - 6 + 7 - 3 - 6)^{18} & := (-6 + 8 + 7 - 1 + 9 - 4 + 7 - 6 - 7 + 3 - 6)^{18} \\ & := (-6 + 8 + 7 + 1 + 9 + 4 - 7 - 6 + 7 - 3 - 6)^{12} & := (6 + 8 + 7 - 1 + 9 - 4 + 7 - 6 - 7 + 3 - 6)^9 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} & := (6+8-7+1+9-4+7-6-7+3-6)^{18} & := (6+8-7+1-9+4+7-6+7+3-6)^{12} \\ & := (6-8+7+1+9-4+7-6-7+3-6)^{36} & := (6-8-7-1+9+4+7-6+7+3-6)^{12} \\ & := (6+8+7+1-9+4+7-6-7+3-6)^{12} & := (-6+8-7-1+9-4-7+6+7+3-6)^{36} \\ & := (6-8+7-1+9+4+7-6-7+3-6)^{12} & := (-6+8+7-1+9-4-7+6+7+3-6)^9 \\ & := (-6+8+7-1+9-4-7+6-7+3-6)^{36} & := (-6+8-7+1+9-4-7+6+7+3-6)^{18} \\ & := (6+8-7+1+9-4-7+6-7+3-6)^{36} & := (6+8-7+1+9-4-7+6+7+3-6)^9 \\ & := (-6+8+7+1+9-4-7+6-7+3-6)^{18} & := (-6-8+7+1+9-4-7+6+7+3-6)^{36} \\ & := (6+8+7+1+9-4-7+6-7+3-6)^9 & := (6+8-7-1-9+4-7+6+7+3-6)^{18} \\ & := (6+8+7-1-9+4-7+6-7+3-6)^{18} & := (6-8+7-1-9+4-7+6+7+3-6)^{36} \\ & := (6+8-7-1+9+4-7+6-7+3-6)^{12} & := (6-8+7+1-9+4-7+6+7+3-6)^{18} \\ & := (6-8+7+1+9+4-7+6-7+3-6)^{12} & := (-6+8+7+1-9+4-7+6+7+3-6)^{12} \\ & := (-6+8-7-1+9-4+7+6-7+3-6)^{36} & := (-6-8+7-1+9+4-7+6+7+3-6)^{12} \\ & := (-6+8+7-1+9-4+7+6-7+3-6)^9 & := (6-8-7+1+9+4-7+6+7+3-6)^{12} \\ & := (-6+8-7+1+9-4+7+6-7+3-6)^{18} & := (6-8+7-1-9-4+7+6+7+3-6)^{12} \\ & := (6+8-7+1+9-4+7+6-7+3-6)^9 & := (-6+8-7-1+9-4+7+6+7+3-6)^9 \\ & := (-6-8+7+1+9-4+7+6-7+3-6)^{36} & := (-6-8-7+1+9-4+7+6+7+3-6)^{36} \\ & := (6+8-7-1-9+4+7+6-7+3-6)^{18} & := (-6-8+7+1+9-4+7+6+7+3-6)^9 \\ & := (6-8+7-1-9+4+7+6-7+3-6)^{36} & := (6-8-7-1-9+4+7+6+7+3-6)^{36} \\ & := (6-8+7+1-9+4+7+6-7+3-6)^{18} & := (-6-8+7-1-9+4+7+6+7+3-6)^{18} \\ & := (-6+8+7+1-9+4+7+6-7+3-6)^{12} & := (6-8+7-1-9+4+7+6+7+3-6)^9 \\ & := (-6-8+7-1+9+4+7+6-7+3-6)^{12} & := (6-8-7+1-9+4+7+6+7+3-6)^{18} \\ & := (6-8-7+1+9+4+7+6-7+3-6)^{12} & := (-6+8-7+1-9+4+7+6+7+3-6)^{12} \\ & := (6+8-7-1+9-4-7-6+7+3-6)^{36} & := (-6-8-7-1+9+4+7+6+7+3-6)^{12} \\ & := (-6+8+7-1+9-4-7-6+7+3-6)^{18} & := (6+8+7-1+9-4-7-6-7-3+6)^{12} \\ & := (6+8+7-1+9-4-7-6+7+3-6)^9 & := (6+8-7-1+9+4-7-6-7-3+6)^{36} \\ & := (6+8-7+1+9-4-7-6+7+3-6)^{18} & := (-6+8+7-1+9+4-7-6-7-3+6)^{18} \\ & := (6-8+7+1+9-4-7-6+7+3-6)^{36} & := (6+8+7-1+9+4-7-6-7-3+6)^9 \\ & := (6+8+7+1-9+4-7-6+7+3-6)^{12} & := (6+8-7+1+9+4-7-6-7-3+6)^{18} \\ & := (6-8+7-1+9+4-7-6+7+3-6)^{12} & := (6-8+7+1+9+4-7-6-7-3+6)^{36} \\ & := (-6+8+7+1-9-4+7-6+7+3-6)^{36} & := (6+8+7-1-9-4+7-6-7-3+6)^{18} \\ & := (-6+8-7-1+9-4+7-6+7+3-6)^{18} & := (6+8-7-1+9-4+7-6-7-3+6)^{12} \\ & := (6+8-7-1+9-4+7-6+7+3-6)^9 & := (6-8+7+1+9-4+7-6-7-3+6)^{12} \\ & := (-6-8+7-1+9-4+7-6+7+3-6)^{36} & := (-6+8+7+1-9+4+7-6-7-3+6)^{36} \\ & := (6-8-7+1+9-4+7-6+7+3-6)^{36} & := (-6+8-7-1+9+4+7-6-7-3+6)^{18} \\ & := (-6-8+7+1+9-4+7-6+7+3-6)^{18} & := (6+8-7-1+9+4+7-6-7-3+6)^9 \\ & := (6-8+7+1+9-4+7-6+7+3-6)^9 & := (-6-8+7-1+9+4+7-6-7-3+6)^{36} \\ & := (6-8+7-1-9+4+7-6+7+3-6)^{18} & := (6-8-7+1+9+4+7-6-7-3+6)^{36} \\ & := (-6+8+7-1-9+4+7-6+7+3-6)^{12} & := (-6-8+7+1+9+4+7-6-7-3+6)^{18} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} & := (6-8+7+1+9+4+7-6-7-3+6)^9 & := (6-8-7+1+9-4+7-6+7-3+6)^{12} \\ & := (6+8+7-1-9-4-7+6-7-3+6)^{36} & := (-6+8-7+1-9+4+7-6+7-3+6)^{36} \\ & := (6+8+7+1-9-4-7+6-7-3+6)^{18} & := (-6+8+7+1-9+4+7-6+7-3+6)^9 \\ & := (6-8+7-1+9-4-7+6-7-3+6)^{18} & := (-6-8-7-1+9+4+7-6+7-3+6)^{36} \\ & := (-6+8+7-1+9-4-7+6-7-3+6)^{12} & := (-6-8+7-1+9+4+7-6+7-3+6)^9 \\ & := (6+8-7+1+9-4-7+6-7-3+6)^{12} & := (-6-8-7+1+9+4+7-6+7-3+6)^{18} \\ & := (-6+8-7-1+9+4-7+6-7-3+6)^{36} & := (6-8-7+1+9+4+7-6+7-3+6)^9 \\ & := (-6+8+7-1+9+4-7+6-7-3+6)^9 & := (6+8-7-1-9-4-7+6+7-3+6)^{36} \\ & := (-6+8-7+1+9+4-7+6-7-3+6)^{18} & := (-6+8+7-1-9-4-7+6+7-3+6)^{18} \\ & := (6+8-7+1+9+4-7+6-7-3+6)^9 & := (6+8+7-1-9-4-7+6+7-3+6)^9 \\ & := (-6-8+7+1+9+4-7+6-7-3+6)^{36} & := (6+8-7+1-9-4-7+6+7-3+6)^{18} \\ & := (6+8-7-1-9-4+7+6-7-3+6)^{36} & := (6-8+7+1-9-4-7+6+7-3+6)^{36} \\ & := (-6+8+7-1-9-4+7+6-7-3+6)^{18} & := (6-8-7-1+9-4-7+6+7-3+6)^{18} \\ & := (6+8+7-1-9-4+7+6-7-3+6)^9 & := (-6+8-7-1+9-4-7+6+7-3+6)^{12} \\ & := (6+8-7+1-9-4+7+6-7-3+6)^{18} & := (-6-8+7+1+9-4-7+6+7-3+6)^{12} \\ & := (6-8+7+1-9-4+7+6-7-3+6)^{36} & := (6-8+7-1-9+4-7+6+7-3+6)^{12} \\ & := (6-8-7-1+9-4+7+6-7-3+6)^{18} & := (-6+8-7-1+9+4-7+6+7-3+6)^9 \\ & := (-6+8-7-1+9-4+7+6-7-3+6)^{12} & := (-6-8-7+1+9+4-7+6+7-3+6)^{36} \\ & := (-6-8+7+1+9-4+7+6-7-3+6)^{12} & := (-6-8+7+1+9+4-7+6+7-3+6)^9 \\ & := (6-8+7-1-9+4+7+6-7-3+6)^{12} & := (-6+8-7-1-9-4+7+6+7-3+6)^{18} \\ & := (-6+8-7-1+9+4+7+6-7-3+6)^9 & := (6+8-7-1-9-4+7+6+7-3+6)^9 \\ & := (6+8-7+1-9-4+7+6-7-3+6)^{36} & := (-6-8+7-1-9-4+7+6+7-3+6)^{36} \\ & := (-6-8+7+1+9+4+7+6-7-3+6)^9 & := (6-8-7+1-9-4+7+6+7-3+6)^{36} \\ & := (6+8+7-1-9-4-7-6+7-3+6)^{18} & := (-6-8+7+1-9-4+7+6+7-3+6)^{18} \\ & := (6+8-7-1+9-4-7-6+7-3+6)^{12} & := (6-8+7+1-9-4+7+6+7-3+6)^9 \\ & := (6-8+7+1+9-4-7-6+7-3+6)^{12} & := (-6-8-7+1+9-4+7+6+7-3+6)^{12} \\ & := (-6+8+7+1-9+4-7-6+7-3+6)^{36} & := (6-8-7-1-9+4+7+6+7-3+6)^{12} \\ & := (-6+8-7-1+9+4-7-6+7-3+6)^{18} & := (-6-8-7+1+9+4+7+6+7-3+6)^9 \\ & := (6+8-7-1+9+4-7-6+7-3+6)^9 & := (-6+8+7-1+9-4-7-6-7+3+6)^{36} \\ & := (-6-8+7-1+9+4-7-6+7-3+6)^{36} & := (6+8-7+1+9-4-7-6-7+3+6)^{36} \\ & := (6-8-7+1+9+4-7-6+7-3+6)^{36} & := (-6+8+7+1+9-4-7-6-7+3+6)^{18} \\ & := (-6-8+7+1+9+4-7-6+7-3+6)^{18} & := (6+8+7+1+9-4-7-6-7+3+6)^9 \\ & := (6-8+7+1+9+4-7-6+7-3+6)^9 & := (6+8+7-1-9+4-7-6-7+3+6)^{18} \\ & := (6+8-7-1-9-4+7-6+7-3+6)^{18} & := (6+8-7-1+9+4-7-6-7+3+6)^{12} \\ & := (6-8+7-1-9-4+7-6+7-3+6)^{36} & := (6-8+7+1+9+4-7-6-7+3+6)^{12} \\ & := (6-8+7+1-9-4+7-6+7-3+6)^{18} & := (-6+8-7-1+9-4+7-6-7+3+6)^{36} \\ & := (-6+8+7+1-9-4+7-6+7-3+6)^{12} & := (-6+8+7-1+9-4+7-6-7+3+6)^9 \\ & := (-6-8+7-1+9-4+7-6+7-3+6)^{12} & := (-6+8-7+1+9-4+7-6-7+3+6)^{18} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} & := (6+8-7+1+9-4+7-6-7+3+6)^9 & := (-6-8+7-1+9+4-7-6+7+3+6)^{12} \\ & := (-6-8+7+1+9-4+7-6-7+3+6)^{36} & := (6-8-7+1+9+4-7-6+7+3+6)^{12} \\ & := (6+8-7-1-9+4+7-6-7+3+6)^{18} & := (6-8+7-1-9-4+7-6+7+3+6)^{12} \\ & := (6-8+7-1-9+4+7-6-7+3+6)^{36} & := (-6+8-7-1+9-4+7-6+7+3+6)^9 \\ & := (6-8+7+1-9+4+7-6-7+3+6)^{18} & := (-6-8-7+1+9-4+7-6+7+3+6)^{36} \\ & := (-6+8+7+1-9+4+7-6-7+3+6)^{12} & := (-6-8+7+1+9-4+7-6+7+3+6)^9 \\ & := (-6-8+7-1+9+4+7-6-7+3+6)^{12} & := (6-8-7-1-9+4+7-6+7+3+6)^{36} \\ & := (6-8-7+1+9+4+7-6-7+3+6)^{12} & := (-6-8+7-1-9+4+7-6+7+3+6)^{18} \\ & := (6+8+7-1-9-4-7+6-7+3+6)^{12} & := (6-8+7-1-9+4+7-6+7+3+6)^9 \\ & := (-6+8-7+1+9-4-7+6-7+3+6)^{36} & := (6-8-7+1-9+4+7-6+7+3+6)^{18} \\ & := (-6+8+7+1+9-4-7+6-7+3+6)^9 & := (-6+8-7+1-9+4+7-6+7+3+6)^{12} \\ & := (6+8-7-1-9+4-7+6-7+3+6)^{36} & := (-6-8-7-1+9+4+7-6+7+3+6)^{12} \\ & := (-6+8+7-1-9+4-7+6-7+3+6)^{18} & := (6+8-7-1-9-4-7+6+7+3+6)^{12} \\ & := (6+8+7-1-9+4-7+6-7+3+6)^9 & := (6-8+7+1-9-4-7+6+7+3+6)^{12} \\ & := (6+8-7+1-9+4-7+6-7+3+6)^{18} & := (-6+8-7+1+9-4-7+6+7+3+6)^9 \\ & := (6-8+7+1-9+4-7+6-7+3+6)^{36} & := (-6+8-7-1-9+4-7+6+7+3+6)^{18} \\ & := (6-8-7-1+9+4-7+6-7+3+6)^{18} & := (6+8-7-1-9+4-7+6+7+3+6)^9 \\ & := (-6+8-7-1+9+4-7+6-7+3+6)^{12} & := (-6-8+7-1-9+4-7+6+7+3+6)^{36} \\ & := (-6-8+7+1+9+4-7+6-7+3+6)^{12} & := (6-8-7+1-9+4-7+6+7+3+6)^{36} \\ & := (6+8-7-1-9-4+7+6-7+3+6)^{12} & := (-6-8+7+1-9+4-7+6+7+3+6)^{18} \\ & := (6-8+7+1-9-4+7+6-7+3+6)^{12} & := (6-8+7+1-9+4-7+6+7+3+6)^9 \\ & := (-6+8-7+1+9-4+7+6-7+3+6)^9 & := (-6-8-7+1+9+4-7+6+7+3+6)^{12} \\ & := (-6+8-7-1-9+4+7+6-7+3+6)^{18} & := (-6-8+7-1-9-4+7+6+7+3+6)^{12} \\ & := (6+8-7-1-9+4+7+6-7+3+6)^9 & := (6-8-7+1-9-4+7+6+7+3+6)^{12} \\ & := (-6-8+7-1-9+4+7+6-7+3+6)^{36} & := (-6-8-7-1-9+4+7+6+7+3+6)^{36} \\ & := (6-8-7+1-9+4+7+6-7+3+6)^{36} & := (-6-8+7-1-9+4+7+6+7+3+6)^9 \\ & := (-6-8+7+1-9+4+7+6-7+3+6)^{18} & := (-6-8-7+1-9+4+7+6+7+3+6)^{18} \\ & := (6-8+7+1-9+4+7+6-7+3+6)^9 & := (6-8-7+1-9+4+7+6+7+3+6)^9 \\ & := (-6-8-7+1+9+4+7+6-7+3+6)^{12} & := (6+8+7+1+9+4+7+6+7+3+6)^6 \\ & := (-6+8-7-1+9-4-7-6+7+3+6)^{36} & := (68+7-1+9-4+7-6-7-3-6)^6 \\ & := (-6+8+7-1+9-4-7-6+7+3+6)^9 & := (68+7+1+9-4-7+6-7-3-6)^6 \\ & := (-6+8-7+1+9-4-7-6+7+3+6)^{18} & := (68-7+1+9-4+7+6-7-3-6)^6 \\ & := (6+8-7+1+9-4-7-6+7+3+6)^9 & := (68+7-1+9-4-7-6+7-3-6)^6 \\ & := (-6-8+7+1+9-4-7-6+7+3+6)^{36} & := (68-7-1+9-4+7-6+7-3-6)^6 \\ & := (6+8-7-1-9+4-7-6+7+3+6)^{18} & := (68-7+1+9-4-7+6+7-3-6)^6 \\ & := (6-8+7-1-9+4-7-6+7+3+6)^{36} & := (68+7-1+9+4-7-6-7+3-6)^6 \\ & := (6-8+7+1-9+4-7-6+7+3+6)^{18} & := (68-7-1+9+4+7-6-7+3-6)^6 \\ & := (-6+8+7+1-9+4-7-6+7+3+6)^{12} & := (68-7+1+9+4-7+6-7+3-6)^6 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} & := (68 + 7 - 1 - 9 - 4 + 7 + 6 - 7 + 3 - 6)^6 & := (-6 - 8 - 7 + 1 - 9 + 47 - 6 - 7 + 3 - 6)^{36} \\ & := (68 - 7 - 1 + 9 + 4 - 7 - 6 + 7 + 3 - 6)^6 & := (-6 - 8 + 7 + 1 - 9 + 47 - 6 - 7 + 3 - 6)^9 \\ & := (68 + 7 - 1 - 9 - 4 - 7 + 6 + 7 + 3 - 6)^6 & := (-6 - 8 - 7 + 1 - 9 + 47 - 6 + 7 + 3 - 6)^9 \\ & := (68 - 7 - 1 - 9 - 4 + 7 + 6 + 7 + 3 - 6)^6 & := (-6 + 8 + 7 + 1 + 9 + 47 - 6 + 7 + 3 - 6)^6 \\ & := (68 + 7 + 1 + 9 - 4 - 7 - 6 - 7 - 3 + 6)^6 & := (-6 - 8 - 7 + 1 - 9 + 47 - 6 - 7 - 3 + 6)^{12} \\ & := (68 - 7 + 1 + 9 - 4 + 7 - 6 - 7 - 3 + 6)^6 & := (6 + 8 - 7 - 1 + 9 + 47 + 6 - 7 - 3 + 6)^6 \\ & := (68 + 7 - 1 - 9 + 4 - 7 + 6 - 7 - 3 + 6)^6 & := (6 - 8 + 7 + 1 + 9 + 47 + 6 - 7 - 3 + 6)^6 \\ & := (68 - 7 - 1 - 9 + 4 + 7 + 6 - 7 - 3 + 6)^6 & := (6 + 8 + 7 + 1 - 9 + 47 - 6 + 7 - 3 + 6)^6 \\ & := (68 - 7 + 1 + 9 - 4 - 7 - 6 + 7 - 3 + 6)^6 & := (6 - 8 + 7 - 1 + 9 + 47 - 6 + 7 - 3 + 6)^6 \\ & := (68 - 7 - 1 - 9 + 4 - 7 + 6 + 7 - 3 + 6)^6 & := (-6 + 8 + 7 + 1 - 9 + 47 + 6 + 7 - 3 + 6)^6 \\ & := (68 - 7 + 1 + 9 + 4 - 7 - 6 - 7 + 3 + 6)^6 & := (-6 - 8 + 7 - 1 + 9 + 47 + 6 + 7 - 3 + 6)^6 \\ & := (68 + 7 - 1 - 9 - 4 + 7 - 6 - 7 + 3 + 6)^6 & := (6 - 8 - 7 + 1 + 9 + 47 + 6 + 7 - 3 + 6)^6 \\ & := (68 + 7 + 1 - 9 - 4 - 7 + 6 - 7 + 3 + 6)^6 & := (6 + 8 + 7 - 1 + 9 - 47 + 6 + 7 + 3 + 6)^{18} \\ & := (68 - 7 + 1 - 9 - 4 + 7 + 6 - 7 + 3 + 6)^6 & := (6 - 8 + 7 - 1 - 9 + 47 + 6 + 7 + 3 + 6)^6 \\ & := (68 + 7 - 1 - 9 - 4 - 7 - 6 + 7 + 3 + 6)^6 & := (-6 - 8 - 7 - 1 - 9 - 4 - 7 + 67 - 3 - 6)^9 \\ & := (68 - 7 - 1 - 9 - 4 + 7 - 6 + 7 + 3 + 6)^6 & := (-6 + 8 + 7 - 1 + 9 - 4 - 7 + 67 - 3 - 6)^6 \\ & := (68 - 7 + 1 - 9 - 4 - 7 + 6 + 7 + 3 + 6)^6 & := (6 + 8 - 7 + 1 + 9 - 4 - 7 + 67 - 3 - 6)^6 \\ & := (-6 + 87 - 1 + 9 + 4 - 7 - 6 - 7 - 3 - 6)^6 & := (-6 + 8 - 7 - 1 + 9 - 4 + 7 + 67 - 3 - 6)^6 \\ & := (6 + 87 - 1 - 9 - 4 + 7 - 6 - 7 - 3 - 6)^6 & := (-6 - 8 + 7 + 1 + 9 - 4 + 7 + 67 - 3 - 6)^6 \\ & := (6 + 87 + 1 - 9 - 4 - 7 + 6 - 7 - 3 - 6)^6 & := (6 - 8 + 7 - 1 - 9 + 4 + 7 + 67 - 3 - 6)^6 \\ & := (-6 + 87 - 1 - 9 - 4 + 7 + 6 - 7 - 3 - 6)^6 & := (6 + 8 + 7 - 1 - 9 - 4 - 7 + 67 + 3 - 6)^6 \\ & := (6 + 87 - 1 - 9 - 4 - 7 - 6 + 7 - 3 - 6)^6 & := (-6 + 8 - 7 - 1 + 9 + 4 - 7 + 67 + 3 - 6)^6 \\ & := (-6 + 87 - 1 - 9 - 4 - 7 + 6 + 7 - 3 - 6)^6 & := (-6 - 8 + 7 + 1 + 9 + 4 - 7 + 67 + 3 - 6)^6 \\ & := (-6 + 87 + 1 + 9 - 4 - 7 - 6 - 7 + 3 - 6)^6 & := (6 + 8 - 7 - 1 - 9 - 4 + 7 + 67 + 3 - 6)^6 \\ & := (6 + 87 - 1 - 9 + 4 - 7 - 6 - 7 + 3 - 6)^6 & := (6 - 8 + 7 + 1 - 9 - 4 + 7 + 67 + 3 - 6)^6 \\ & := (-6 + 87 - 1 - 9 + 4 - 7 + 6 - 7 + 3 - 6)^6 & := (-6 - 8 - 7 + 1 + 9 + 4 + 7 + 67 + 3 - 6)^6 \\ & := (6 + 87 + 1 - 9 - 4 - 7 - 6 - 7 - 3 + 6)^6 & := (-6 + 8 - 7 + 1 + 9 - 4 - 7 + 67 - 3 + 6)^6 \\ & := (-6 + 87 - 1 - 9 - 4 + 7 - 6 - 7 - 3 + 6)^6 & := (6 + 8 - 7 - 1 - 9 + 4 - 7 + 67 - 3 + 6)^6 \\ & := (-6 + 87 + 1 - 9 - 4 - 7 + 6 - 7 - 3 + 6)^6 & := (6 - 8 + 7 + 1 - 9 + 4 - 7 + 67 - 3 + 6)^6 \\ & := (-6 + 87 - 1 - 9 - 4 - 7 - 6 + 7 - 3 + 6)^6 & := (-6 - 8 + 7 - 1 - 9 + 4 + 7 + 67 - 3 + 6)^6 \\ & := (-6 + 87 - 1 - 9 + 4 - 7 - 6 - 7 + 3 + 6)^6 & := (6 - 8 - 7 + 1 - 9 + 4 + 7 + 67 - 3 + 6)^6 \\ & := (-6 - 8 + 7 - 1 - 9 + 47 - 6 - 7 - 3 - 6)^{12} & := (-6 + 8 + 7 - 1 - 9 - 4 - 7 + 67 + 3 + 6)^6 \\ & := (6 - 8 - 7 + 1 - 9 + 47 - 6 - 7 - 3 - 6)^{12} & := (6 + 8 - 7 + 1 - 9 - 4 - 7 + 67 + 3 + 6)^6 \\ & := (-6 - 8 - 7 + 1 - 9 + 47 + 6 - 7 - 3 - 6)^{12} & := (6 - 8 - 7 - 1 + 9 - 4 - 7 + 67 + 3 + 6)^6 \\ & := (-6 - 8 - 7 - 1 - 9 + 47 - 6 + 7 - 3 - 6)^{12} & := (-6 + 8 - 7 - 1 - 9 - 4 + 7 + 67 + 3 + 6)^6 \\ & := (6 + 8 + 7 + 1 - 9 + 47 + 6 + 7 - 3 - 6)^6 & := (-6 - 8 + 7 + 1 - 9 - 4 + 7 + 67 + 3 + 6)^6 \\ & := (6 - 8 + 7 - 1 + 9 + 47 + 6 + 7 - 3 - 6)^6 & := (68 - 7 + 1 + 9 - 47 - 6 - 7 - 3 - 6)^{36} \\ & := (-6 + 8 - 7 - 1 - 9 + 47 - 6 - 7 + 3 - 6)^9 & := (68 + 7 + 1 + 9 - 47 - 6 - 7 - 3 - 6)^9 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} & := (68 + 7 - 1 - 9 - 47 + 6 - 7 - 3 - 6)^{12} & := (68 - 7 + 1 + 9 - 4 + 7 - 67 + 3 - 6)^{18} \\ & := (68 - 7 + 1 + 9 - 47 - 6 + 7 - 3 - 6)^9 & := (68 + 7 + 1 - 9 + 4 + 7 - 67 + 3 - 6)^{12} \\ & := (68 - 7 - 1 - 9 - 47 + 6 + 7 - 3 - 6)^{12} & := (-68 + 7 + 1 + 9 - 4 - 7 + 67 + 3 - 6)^{36} \\ & := (68 + 7 - 1 - 9 - 47 - 6 - 7 + 3 - 6)^{36} & := (-68 + 7 - 1 + 9 + 4 - 7 + 67 + 3 - 6)^{12} \\ & := (68 + 7 + 1 - 9 - 47 - 6 - 7 + 3 - 6)^{18} & := (-68 - 7 + 1 + 9 - 4 + 7 + 67 + 3 - 6)^{36} \\ & := (68 - 7 + 1 + 9 - 47 - 6 - 7 + 3 - 6)^{12} & := (-68 + 7 + 1 + 9 - 4 + 7 + 67 + 3 - 6)^9 \\ & := (68 - 7 + 1 - 9 - 47 + 6 - 7 + 3 - 6)^{36} & := (-68 + 7 - 1 - 9 + 4 + 7 + 67 + 3 - 6)^{18} \\ & := (68 + 7 + 1 - 9 - 47 + 6 - 7 + 3 - 6)^9 & := (-68 - 7 - 1 + 9 + 4 + 7 + 67 + 3 - 6)^{12} \\ & := (68 - 7 - 1 - 9 - 47 - 6 + 7 + 3 - 6)^{36} & := (68 + 7 - 1 + 9 - 4 - 7 - 67 - 3 + 6)^{12} \\ & := (68 + 7 - 1 - 9 - 47 - 6 + 7 + 3 - 6)^9 & := (68 - 7 - 1 + 9 + 4 - 7 - 67 - 3 + 6)^{36} \\ & := (68 - 7 + 1 - 9 - 47 - 6 + 7 + 3 - 6)^{18} & := (68 + 7 - 1 + 9 + 4 - 7 - 67 - 3 + 6)^9 \\ & := (68 - 7 + 1 - 9 - 47 + 6 + 7 + 3 - 6)^9 & := (68 - 7 + 1 + 9 + 4 - 7 - 67 - 3 + 6)^{18} \\ & := (-68 + 7 - 1 + 9 + 47 + 6 + 7 + 3 - 6)^{18} & := (68 + 7 - 1 - 9 - 4 + 7 - 67 - 3 + 6)^{18} \\ & := (68 + 7 - 1 - 9 - 47 - 6 - 7 - 3 + 6)^{12} & := (68 - 7 - 1 + 9 - 4 + 7 - 67 - 3 + 6)^{12} \\ & := (68 - 7 + 1 - 9 - 47 + 6 - 7 - 3 + 6)^{12} & := (68 - 7 - 1 + 9 + 4 + 7 - 67 - 3 + 6)^9 \\ & := (68 - 7 - 1 - 9 - 47 - 6 + 7 - 3 + 6)^{12} & := (-68 + 7 + 1 + 9 - 4 - 7 + 67 - 3 + 6)^{12} \\ & := (68 - 7 + 1 - 9 - 47 - 6 - 7 + 3 + 6)^{36} & := (-68 - 7 + 1 + 9 + 4 - 7 + 67 - 3 + 6)^{36} \\ & := (68 + 7 + 1 - 9 - 47 - 6 - 7 + 3 + 6)^9 & := (-68 + 7 + 1 + 9 + 4 - 7 + 67 - 3 + 6)^9 \\ & := (-68 + 7 - 1 + 9 + 47 + 6 - 7 + 3 + 6)^{36} & := (-68 + 7 - 1 - 9 - 4 + 7 + 67 - 3 + 6)^{36} \\ & := (-68 + 7 + 1 + 9 + 47 + 6 - 7 + 3 + 6)^{18} & := (-68 + 7 + 1 - 9 - 4 + 7 + 67 - 3 + 6)^{18} \\ & := (68 - 7 + 1 - 9 - 47 - 6 + 7 + 3 + 6)^9 & := (-68 - 7 + 1 + 9 - 4 + 7 + 67 - 3 + 6)^{12} \\ & := (-68 + 7 - 1 + 9 + 47 - 6 + 7 + 3 + 6)^{18} & := (-68 - 7 + 1 + 9 + 4 + 7 + 67 - 3 + 6)^9 \\ & := (-68 - 7 - 1 + 9 + 47 + 6 + 7 + 3 + 6)^{36} & := (68 - 7 + 1 + 9 - 4 - 7 - 67 + 3 + 6)^{36} \\ & := (-68 + 7 - 1 + 9 + 47 + 6 + 7 + 3 + 6)^9 & := (68 + 7 + 1 + 9 - 4 - 7 - 67 + 3 + 6)^9 \\ & := (-68 - 7 + 1 + 9 + 47 + 6 + 7 + 3 + 6)^{18} & := (68 + 7 - 1 - 9 + 4 - 7 - 67 + 3 + 6)^{18} \\ & := (68 + 7 - 1 + 9 + 4 - 7 - 67 - 3 - 6)^{18} & := (68 - 7 - 1 + 9 + 4 - 7 - 67 + 3 + 6)^{12} \\ & := (68 + 7 + 1 - 9 + 4 + 7 - 67 - 3 - 6)^{36} & := (68 - 7 + 1 + 9 - 4 + 7 - 67 + 3 + 6)^9 \\ & := (68 - 7 - 1 + 9 + 4 + 7 - 67 - 3 - 6)^{18} & := (68 - 7 - 1 - 9 + 4 + 7 - 67 + 3 + 6)^{18} \\ & := (-68 + 7 - 1 + 9 + 4 - 7 + 67 - 3 - 6)^{36} & := (-68 + 7 - 1 - 9 + 4 - 7 + 67 + 3 + 6)^{36} \\ & := (-68 + 7 + 1 + 9 + 4 - 7 + 67 - 3 - 6)^{18} & := (-68 + 7 + 1 - 9 + 4 - 7 + 67 + 3 + 6)^{18} \\ & := (-68 + 7 - 1 + 9 - 4 + 7 + 67 - 3 - 6)^{12} & := (-68 - 7 + 1 + 9 + 4 - 7 + 67 + 3 + 6)^{12} \\ & := (-68 - 7 - 1 + 9 + 4 + 7 + 67 - 3 - 6)^{36} & := (-68 + 7 - 1 - 9 - 4 + 7 + 67 + 3 + 6)^{12} \\ & := (-68 + 7 - 1 + 9 + 4 + 7 + 67 - 3 - 6)^9 & := (-68 - 7 - 1 - 9 + 4 + 7 + 67 + 3 + 6)^{36} \\ & := (-68 - 7 + 1 + 9 + 4 + 7 + 67 - 3 - 6)^{18} & := (-68 + 7 - 1 - 9 + 4 + 7 + 67 + 3 + 6)^9 \\ & := (68 + 7 - 1 + 9 - 4 - 7 - 67 + 3 - 6)^{36} & := (-68 - 7 + 1 - 9 + 4 + 7 + 67 + 3 + 6)^{18} \\ & := (68 + 7 + 1 + 9 - 4 - 7 - 67 + 3 - 6)^{18} & := (-6 + 87 - 1 - 9 - 47 - 6 - 7 - 3 - 6)^{36} \\ & := (68 - 7 - 1 + 9 - 4 + 7 - 67 + 3 - 6)^{36} & := (-6 + 87 + 1 - 9 - 47 - 6 - 7 - 3 - 6)^{18} \\ & := (68 + 7 - 1 + 9 - 4 + 7 - 67 + 3 - 6)^9 & := (6 + 87 + 1 - 9 - 47 - 6 - 7 - 3 - 6)^9 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} & := (-6+87+1-9-47+6-7-3-6)^9 & := (6-8-71+94-7+6-7-3-6)^{18} \\ & := (-6+87-1-9-47-6+7-3-6)^9 & := (-6+8-71+94-7+6-7-3-6)^{12} \\ & := (-6+87-1-9-47-6-7+3-6)^{12} & := (-6-8-71+94+7-6+7-3-6)^{12} \\ & := (6+87-1+9-47+6+7+3-6)^6 & := (6+8+71-94+7+6+7-3-6)^{36} \\ & := (-6+87+1-9-47-6-7-3+6)^9 & := (-6+8-71+94-7-6-7+3-6)^{36} \\ & := (6+87+1+9-47+6-7+3+6)^6 & := (-6+8-71+94+7-6-7+3-6)^9 \\ & := (6+87-1+9-47-6+7+3+6)^6 & := (-6+8-71+94-7-6+7+3-6)^9 \\ & := (-6+87-1+9-47+6+7+3+6)^6 & := (6+8+71-94+7+6+7+3-6)^{12} \\ & := (-6+87-1+9-4-7-67-3-6)^{36} & := (6-8-71+94-7-6-7-3+6)^{18} \\ & := (-6+87+1+9-4-7-67-3-6)^{18} & := (-6+8-71+94-7-6-7-3+6)^{12} \\ & := (6+87+1+9-4-7-67-3-6)^9 & := (-6-8-71+94-7+6-7-3+6)^{18} \\ & := (6+87-1-9+4-7-67-3-6)^{18} & := (6-8-71+94-7+6-7-3+6)^9 \\ & := (-6+87-1+9-4+7-67-3-6)^9 & := (6+8+71-94+7-6+7-3+6)^{36} \\ & := (-6+87+1-9+4+7-67-3-6)^{12} & := (-6+8+71-94+7+6+7-3+6)^{36} \\ & := (6+87-1-9-4-7-67+3-6)^{36} & := (6+8+71-94+7-6+7+3+6)^{12} \\ & := (6+87+1-9-4-7-67+3-6)^{18} & := (6-8+71-94+7+6+7+3+6)^{18} \\ & := (-6+87-1+9-4-7-67+3-6)^{12} & := (-6+8+71-94+7+6+7+3+6)^{12} \\ & := (-6+87-1+9+4-7-67+3-6)^9 & := (6+8-71+9-4+76-7-3-6)^{12} \\ & := (-6+87-1-9-4+7-67+3-6)^{18} & := (-6+8-71+9+4+76-7-3-6)^{18} \\ & := (6+87-1-9-4+7-67+3-6)^9 & := (6+8-71+9+4+76-7-3-6)^9 \\ & := (6-87-1+9+4+7+67+3-6)^{36} & := (6+8+71-9+4-76+7-3-6)^{36} \\ & := (6-87+1+9+4+7+67+3-6)^{18} & := (6-8+71+9+4-76+7-3-6)^{18} \\ & := (6+87-1-9-4-7-67-3+6)^{12} & := (-6+8+71+9+4-76+7-3-6)^{12} \\ & := (-6+87+1+9-4-7-67-3+6)^9 & := (6+8-71-9-4+76+7-3-6)^{18} \\ & := (-6+87-1-9+4-7-67-3+6)^{18} & := (-6-8-71+9+4+76+7-3-6)^{36} \\ & := (6+87-1-9+4-7-67-3+6)^9 & := (6+8+71+9-4-76-7+3-6)^{18} \\ & := (6-87+1+9-4+7+67-3+6)^{36} & := (-6+8-71+9-4+76-7+3-6)^{36} \\ & := (6-87-1+9+4+7+67-3+6)^{12} & := (6+8-71-9+4+76-7+3-6)^{18} \\ & := (-6+87-1-9-4-7-67+3+6)^{36} & := (6-8+71+9-4-76+7+3-6)^{36} \\ & := (-6+87+1-9-4-7-67+3+6)^{18} & := (6+8+71-9+4-76+7+3-6)^{12} \\ & := (6+87+1-9-4-7-67+3+6)^9 & := (-6+8-71+9-4+76+7+3-6)^9 \\ & := (-6+87-1-9-4+7-67+3+6)^9 & := (6-8-71-9+4+76+7+3-6)^{36} \\ & := (6-87+1+9+4-7+67+3+6)^{36} & := (-6-8-71+9+4+76+7+3-6)^{12} \\ & := (6-87+1+9-4+7+67+3+6)^{12} & := (6-8+71+9+4-76-7-3+6)^{36} \\ & := (-6-87-1+9+4+7+67+3+6)^{36} & := (6+8-71-9-4+76-7-3+6)^{36} \\ & := (-6-87+1+9+4+7+67+3+6)^{18} & := (6-8-71+9-4+76-7-3+6)^{18} \\ & := (6-87+1+9+4+7+67+3+6)^9 & := (-6+8-71+9-4+76-7-3+6)^{12} \\ & := (6+8-71+94-7-6-7-3-6)^{12} & := (-6+8-71+9+4+76-7-3+6)^9 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} & := (6-8+71+9-4-76+7-3+6)^{12} & := (6-8+71+9+4+7-6-73+6)^9 \\ & := (-6+8+71-9+4-76+7-3+6)^{36} & := (6+8+71-9-4-7+6-73+6)^{18} \\ & := (-6-8+71+9+4-76+7-3+6)^{18} & := (-6-8+71+9+4-7+6-73+6)^{36} \\ & := (6-8+71+9+4-76+7-3+6)^9 & := (6-8+71-9-4+7+6-73+6)^{36} \\ & := (-6+8-71-9-4+76+7-3+6)^{18} & := (-6-8+71+9-4+7+6-73+6)^{12} \\ & := (6+8-71-9-4+76+7-3+6)^9 & := (-6-8+71+9+4+7+6-73+6)^9 \\ & := (6-8-71-9+4+76+7-3+6)^{12} & := (-6+8-71+9-4-7-6+73+6)^{36} \\ & := (-6+8+71+9-4-76-7+3+6)^{18} & := (6+8-71-9+4-7-6+73+6)^{18} \\ & := (6+8+71+9-4-76-7+3+6)^9 & := (-6+8-71+9-4+7-6+73+6)^9 \\ & := (6-8+71+9+4-76-7+3+6)^{12} & := (6-8-71-9+4+7-6+73+6)^{36} \\ & := (6+8-71-9-4+76-7+3+6)^{12} & := (-6-8-71+9+4+7-6+73+6)^{12} \\ & := (-6+8-71-9+4+76-7+3+6)^{18} & := (6+8-71-9-4-7+6+73+6)^{12} \\ & := (6+8-71-9+4+76-7+3+6)^9 & := (-6+8-71-9+4-7+6+73+6)^{18} \\ & := (-6-8+71+9-4-76+7+3+6)^{36} & := (6+8-71-9+4-7+6+73+6)^9 \\ & := (6-8+71-9+4-76+7+3+6)^{18} & := (-6-8-71-9+4+7+6+73+6)^{36} \\ & := (-6+8+71-9+4-76+7+3+6)^{12} & := (-6+8+71-9-4-7-6-7-36)^{18} \\ & := (-6-8-71-9+4+76+7+3+6)^{36} & := (6+8+71-9-4-7-6-7-36)^9 \\ & := (6+8+71-9+4+7-6-73-6)^{36} & := (6-8+71-9+4-7-6-7-36)^{12} \\ & := (6-8+71+9+4+7-6-73-6)^{18} & := (-6-8+71-9-4+7-6-7-36)^{36} \\ & := (-6+8+71+9+4+7-6-73-6)^{12} & := (-6+8+71-9-4-7+6-7-36)^9 \\ & := (6-8+71+9+4-7+6-73-6)^{36} & := (-6-8+71-9+4-7+6-7-36)^{12} \\ & := (6-8+71+9-4+7+6-73-6)^{12} & := (-6-8+71-9-4-7-6+7-36)^{36} \\ & := (-6+8+71-9+4+7+6-73-6)^{36} & := (-6-8+71-9-4+7-6+7-36)^9 \\ & := (-6-8+71+9+4+7+6-73-6)^{18} & := (6+8+71-9+4+7+6+7-36)^6 \\ & := (6-8+71+9+4+7+6-73-6)^9 & := (6+8-71+9-4+7+6+7+36)^{18} \\ & := (6+8-71+9-4-7-6+73-6)^{36} & := (-6-8-7-19-4+76-7-3-6)^9 \\ & := (-6+8-71+9-4+7-6+73-6)^{18} & := (6-8+7-19+4+76+7-3-6)^6 \\ & := (6+8-71+9-4+7-6+73-6)^9 & := (6+8+7-19-4+76-7+3-6)^6 \\ & := (6-8-71+9+4+7-6+73-6)^{12} & := (6+8-7-19-4+76+7+3-6)^6 \\ & := (-6+8-71+9-4-7+6+73-6)^{36} & := (6+8-7-19+4+76-7-3+6)^6 \\ & := (6+8-71-9+4-7+6+73-6)^{18} & := (-6-8+7-19+4+76+7-3+6)^6 \\ & := (-6+8-71+9-4+7+6+73-6)^9 & := (-6+8+7-19-4+76-7+3+6)^6 \\ & := (6-8-71-9+4+7+6+73-6)^{36} & := (-6+8-7-19-4+76+7+3+6)^6 \\ & := (-6-8-71+9+4+7+6+73-6)^{12} & := (-6+8-7+19-4-7-6+73-6)^6 \\ & := (6-8+71+9+4-7-6-73+6)^{36} & := (6+8+7-19-4-7+6+73-6)^6 \\ & := (6-8+71+9-4+7-6-73+6)^{12} & := (6+8-7-19-4+7+6+73-6)^6 \\ & := (-6+8+71-9+4+7-6-73+6)^{36} & := (6+8+7-19-4-7-6+73+6)^6 \\ & := (-6-8+71+9+4+7-6-73+6)^{18} & := (6+8-7-19-4+7-6+73+6)^6 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} & := (-6+8+7-19-4-7+6+73+6)^6 & := (-6+8-7+1+94-76-7+3-6)^{18} \\ & := (-6+8-7-19-4+7+6+73+6)^6 & := (6+8-7+1+94-76-7+3-6)^9 \\ & := (6+8+7+19+4+7-6-7-36)^{36} & := (-6-8+7+1+94-76-7+3-6)^{36} \\ & := (-6+8+7+19+4+7+6-7-36)^{36} & := (-6+8-7-1+94-76+7+3-6)^9 \\ & := (6+8+7+19+4-7-6+7-36)^{36} & := (-6-8-7+1+94-76+7+3-6)^{36} \\ & := (6+8+7+19-4+7-6+7-36)^{12} & := (-6-8+7+1+94-76+7+3-6)^9 \\ & := (6+8-7+19+4+7-6+7-36)^{36} & := (6+8+7+1-94+76+7+3-6)^{12} \\ & := (-6+8+7+19+4+7-6+7-36)^{18} & := (6-8-7-1+94-76-7-3+6)^{18} \\ & := (6+8+7+19+4+7-6+7-36)^9 & := (-6+8-7-1+94-76-7-3+6)^{12} \\ & := (-6+8+7+19+4-7+6+7-36)^{36} & := (-6-8+7+1+94-76-7-3+6)^{12} \\ & := (6-8+7+19-4+7+6+7-36)^{18} & := (-6-8-7+1+94-76+7-3+6)^{12} \\ & := (-6+8+7+19-4+7+6+7-36)^{12} & := (-6+8+7+1-94+76+7-3+6)^{36} \\ & := (-6+8-7+19+4+7+6+7-36)^{36} & := (-6+8-7+1+94-76-7+3+6)^9 \\ & := (-6+8+7+19+4+7+6+7-36)^9 & := (6+8+7-1-94+76-7+3+6)^{18} \\ & := (-6+8+7-19-4-7-6-7+36)^{36} & := (6+8-7-1-94+76+7+3+6)^{18} \\ & := (6+8-7-19+4-7-6-7+36)^{12} & := (6-8+7-1-94+76+7+3+6)^{36} \\ & := (-6+8-7-19-4+7-6-7+36)^{36} & := (6-8+7+1-94+76+7+3+6)^{18} \\ & := (-6+8+7-19-4+7-6-7+36)^9 & := (-6+8+7+1-94+76+7+3+6)^{12} \\ & := (-6-8+7-19+4+7-6-7+36)^{12} & := (6+8-7-1+94-7-6-73-6)^{12} \\ & := (6+8+7+19-4-7+6-7+36)^6 & := (6-8+7+1+94-7-6-73-6)^{12} \\ & := (6-8-7-19+4-7+6-7+36)^{18} & := (-6-8+7-1+94+7-6-73-6)^{12} \\ & := (-6+8-7-19+4-7+6-7+36)^{12} & := (6-8-7+1+94+7-6-73-6)^{12} \\ & := (6+8-7+19-4+7+6-7+36)^6 & := (6-8-7-1+94-7+6-73-6)^{18} \\ & := (-6+8-7-19-4-7-6+7+36)^{36} & := (-6+8-7-1+94-7+6-73-6)^{12} \\ & := (-6+8+7-19-4-7-6+7+36)^9 & := (-6-8+7+1+94-7+6-73-6)^{12} \\ & := (-6-8+7-19+4-7-6+7+36)^{12} & := (-6-8-7+1+94+7+6-73-6)^{12} \\ & := (-6+8-7-19-4+7-6+7+36)^9 & := (6+8+7+1-94+7+6+73-6)^{12} \\ & := (6-8+7+19-4+7-6+7+36)^6 & := (6-8-7-1+94-7-6-73+6)^{18} \\ & := (-6-8-7-19+4+7-6+7+36)^{12} & := (-6+8-7-1+94-7-6-73+6)^{12} \\ & := (6+8-7+19-4-7+6+7+36)^6 & := (-6-8+7+1+94-7-6-73+6)^{12} \\ & := (-6-8+7+19-4+7+6+7+36)^6 & := (-6-8-7+1+94+7-6-73+6)^{12} \\ & := (6+8-7-1+94-76-7-3-6)^{12} & := (-6-8-7-1+94-7+6-73+6)^{18} \\ & := (6-8+7+1+94-76-7-3-6)^{12} & := (6-8-7-1+94-7+6-73+6)^9 \\ & := (-6-8+7-1+94-76+7-3-6)^{12} & := (6+8+7+1-94+7-6+73+6)^{12} \\ & := (6-8-7+1+94-76+7-3-6)^{12} & := (6+8+7-1-94-7+6+73+6)^{18} \\ & := (6+8+7+1-94+76+7-3-6)^{36} & := (6+8-7-1-94+7+6+73+6)^{18} \\ & := (-6+8-7-1+94-76-7+3-6)^{36} & := (6-8+7-1-94+7+6+73+6)^{36} \\ & := (-6+8+7-1+94-76-7+3-6)^9 & := (6-8+7+1-94+7+6+73+6)^{18} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} & := (-6+8+7+1-94+7+6+73+6)^{12} & := (6+8-7+1+9-4-76+73-6)^{18} \\ & := (-6-8-7-1+94-7-6-7-36)^9 & := (6-8+7+1+9-4-76+73-6)^{36} \\ & := (6+8+7+1+9+47-67-3-6)^{36} & := (6+8+7+1-9+4-76+73-6)^{12} \\ & := (6+8-7-1-9-47+67-3-6)^{12} & := (6-8+7-1+9+4-76+73-6)^{12} \\ & := (6-8+7+1-9-47+67-3-6)^{12} & := (6+8-7-1-9-4+76-73+6)^{36} \\ & := (-6+8-7+1+9-47+67-3-6)^9 & := (-6+8+7-1-9-4+76-73+6)^{18} \\ & := (6+8+7+1+9+47-67+3-6)^{12} & := (6+8+7-1-9-4+76-73+6)^9 \\ & := (-6+8-7-1-9-47+67+3-6)^{36} & := (6+8-7+1-9-4+76-73+6)^{18} \\ & := (-6+8+7-1-9-47+67+3-6)^9 & := (6-8+7+1-9-4+76-73+6)^{36} \\ & := (-6+8-7+1-9-47+67+3-6)^{18} & := (6-8-7-1+9-4+76-73+6)^{18} \\ & := (6+8-7+1-9-47+67+3-6)^9 & := (-6+8-7-1+9-4+76-73+6)^{12} \\ & := (-6-8+7+1-9-47+67+3-6)^{36} & := (-6-8+7+1+9-4+76-73+6)^{12} \\ & := (-6-8-7-1+9-47+67+3-6)^{18} & := (6-8+7-1-9+4+76-73+6)^{12} \\ & := (6-8-7-1+9-47+67+3-6)^9 & := (-6+8-7-1+9+4+76-73+6)^9 \\ & := (-6+8+7+1+9+47-67-3+6)^{36} & := (-6-8-7+1+9+4+76-73+6)^{36} \\ & := (6-8-7-1-9-47+67-3+6)^{18} & := (-6-8+7+1+9+4+76-73+6)^9 \\ & := (-6+8-7-1-9-47+67-3+6)^{12} & := (-6+8-7-1+9-4-76+73+6)^{36} \\ & := (-6-8+7+1-9-47+67-3+6)^{12} & := (-6+8+7-1+9-4-76+73+6)^9 \\ & := (6+8+7+1-9+47-67+3+6)^{36} & := (-6+8-7+1+9-4-76+73+6)^{18} \\ & := (6+8-7-1+9+47-67+3+6)^{18} & := (6+8-7+1+9-4-76+73+6)^9 \\ & := (6-8+7-1+9+47-67+3+6)^{36} & := (-6-8+7+1+9-4-76+73+6)^{36} \\ & := (6-8+7+1+9+47-67+3+6)^{18} & := (6+8-7-1-9+4-76+73+6)^{18} \\ & := (-6+8+7+1+9+47-67+3+6)^{12} & := (6-8+7-1-9+4-76+73+6)^{36} \\ & := (-6+8-7+1-9-47+67+3+6)^9 & := (6-8+7+1-9+4-76+73+6)^{18} \\ & := (-6-8-7-1+9-47+67+3+6)^9 & := (-6+8+7+1-9+4-76+73+6)^{12} \\ & := (6+8+7-1-9-4+76-73-6)^{18} & := (-6-8+7-1+9+4-76+73+6)^{12} \\ & := (6+8-7-1+9-4+76-73-6)^{12} & := (6-8-7+1+9+4-76+73+6)^{12} \\ & := (6-8+7+1+9-4+76-73-6)^{12} & := (-6+8-7+1-9-4+76-7-36)^9 \\ & := (-6+8+7+1-9+4+76-73-6)^{36} & := (-6-8-7-1+9-4+76-7-36)^9 \\ & := (-6+8-7-1+9+4+76-73-6)^{18} & := (-6-8-7+1-9+4+76-7-36)^{12} \\ & := (6+8-7-1+9+4+76-73-6)^9 & := (6+8+7+1-9+4+76+7-36)^6 \\ & := (-6-8+7-1+9+4+76-73-6)^{36} & := (6-8+7-1+9+4+76+7-36)^6 \\ & := (6-8-7+1+9+4+76-73-6)^{36} & := (6+8+7+1+9+4-76+7+36)^{36} \\ & := (-6-8+7+1+9+4+76-73-6)^{18} & := (68+71-94-7-6-7-3-6)^9 \\ & := (6-8+7+1+9+4+76-73-6)^9 & := (-68+71-9-4+76+7-3-6)^6 \\ & := (6+8-7-1+9-4-76+73-6)^{36} & := (-68+71-9+4+76-7+3-6)^6 \\ & := (-6+8+7-1+9-4-76+73-6)^{18} & := (68-71-9-4+76+7+3-6)^6 \\ & := (6+8+7-1+9-4-76+73-6)^9 & := (68+71+9-4-76-7-3+6)^6 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} & := (68 - 71 - 9 + 4 + 76 - 7 - 3 + 6)^6 & := (68 + 7 - 19 + 4 - 7 - 6 - 7 - 36)^{18} \\ & := (68 + 71 + 9 - 4 - 7 + 6 - 73 - 6)^6 & := (68 - 7 - 19 + 4 + 7 - 6 - 7 - 36)^{18} \\ & := (68 - 71 + 9 + 4 - 7 - 6 + 73 - 6)^6 & := (68 + 7 - 19 - 4 - 7 + 6 - 7 - 36)^{12} \\ & := (-68 + 71 - 9 + 4 - 7 + 6 + 73 - 6)^6 & := (68 - 7 - 19 + 4 - 7 + 6 - 7 - 36)^{36} \\ & := (68 - 71 - 9 - 4 + 7 + 6 + 73 - 6)^6 & := (68 + 7 - 19 + 4 - 7 + 6 - 7 - 36)^9 \\ & := (68 + 71 + 9 - 4 - 7 - 6 - 73 + 6)^6 & := (68 - 7 - 19 - 4 + 7 + 6 - 7 - 36)^{12} \\ & := (-68 + 71 - 9 + 4 - 7 - 6 + 73 + 6)^6 & := (68 - 7 - 19 + 4 + 7 + 6 - 7 - 36)^9 \\ & := (68 - 71 - 9 - 4 + 7 - 6 + 73 + 6)^6 & := (68 - 7 - 19 + 4 - 7 - 6 + 7 - 36)^{18} \\ & := (68 - 71 - 9 + 4 - 7 - 6 - 7 + 36)^{12} & := (68 - 7 - 19 - 4 - 7 + 6 + 7 - 36)^{12} \\ & := (-68 + 71 + 9 - 4 + 7 + 6 + 7 + 36)^6 & := (68 - 7 - 19 + 4 - 7 + 6 + 7 - 36)^9 \\ & := (-68 - 7 + 19 + 4 + 76 - 7 - 3 - 6)^{12} & := (-68 + 7 + 19 + 4 + 7 + 6 - 7 + 36)^{18} \\ & := (68 + 7 + 19 - 4 - 76 - 7 + 3 - 6)^{18} & := (-68 + 7 + 19 + 4 - 7 + 6 + 7 + 36)^{18} \\ & := (68 - 7 + 19 - 4 - 76 + 7 + 3 - 6)^{18} & := (-68 - 7 + 19 + 4 + 7 + 6 + 7 + 36)^{18} \\ & := (-68 + 7 - 19 + 4 + 76 + 7 + 3 - 6)^{18} & := (68 - 7 + 1 + 94 - 76 - 7 - 3 - 6)^6 \\ & := (68 - 7 + 19 + 4 - 76 - 7 - 3 + 6)^{18} & := (68 - 7 + 1 + 94 - 7 - 6 - 73 - 6)^6 \\ & := (-68 + 7 - 19 - 4 + 76 + 7 - 3 + 6)^{36} & := (-68 + 7 - 1 + 94 + 7 + 6 - 7 - 36)^{36} \\ & := (68 - 7 + 19 - 4 - 76 - 7 + 3 + 6)^{36} & := (-68 + 7 + 1 + 94 + 7 + 6 - 7 - 36)^{18} \\ & := (68 + 7 + 19 - 4 - 76 - 7 + 3 + 6)^9 & := (-68 + 7 - 1 + 94 + 7 - 6 + 7 - 36)^{18} \\ & := (-68 + 7 - 19 + 4 + 76 - 7 + 3 + 6)^{36} & := (-68 + 7 - 1 + 94 - 7 + 6 + 7 - 36)^{36} \\ & := (68 - 7 + 19 - 4 - 76 + 7 + 3 + 6)^9 & := (-68 + 7 + 1 + 94 - 7 + 6 + 7 - 36)^{18} \\ & := (-68 + 7 - 19 - 4 + 76 + 7 + 3 + 6)^{12} & := (-68 - 7 - 1 + 94 + 7 + 6 + 7 - 36)^{36} \\ & := (-68 - 7 - 19 + 4 + 76 + 7 + 3 + 6)^{36} & := (-68 + 7 - 1 + 94 + 7 + 6 + 7 - 36)^9 \\ & := (-68 + 7 - 19 + 4 + 76 + 7 + 3 + 6)^9 & := (-68 - 7 + 1 + 94 + 7 + 6 + 7 - 36)^{18} \\ & := (68 - 7 + 19 + 4 - 7 + 6 - 73 - 6)^{18} & := (-68 + 7 + 1 + 94 + 7 - 6 - 7 + 36)^6 \\ & := (-68 + 7 + 19 - 4 - 7 - 6 + 73 - 6)^{12} & := (68 + 7 - 1 - 94 - 7 + 6 - 7 + 36)^{12} \\ & := (-68 - 7 + 19 + 4 - 7 - 6 + 73 - 6)^{36} & := (68 - 7 - 1 - 94 + 7 + 6 - 7 + 36)^{12} \\ & := (-68 + 7 + 19 + 4 - 7 - 6 + 73 - 6)^9 & := (-68 + 7 + 1 + 94 - 7 - 6 + 7 + 36)^6 \\ & := (-68 - 7 + 19 - 4 + 7 - 6 + 73 - 6)^{12} & := (-68 - 7 + 1 + 94 + 7 - 6 + 7 + 36)^6 \\ & := (-68 - 7 + 19 + 4 + 7 - 6 + 73 - 6)^9 & := (68 - 7 - 1 - 94 - 7 + 6 + 7 + 36)^{12} \\ & := (-68 + 7 - 19 + 4 + 7 + 6 + 73 - 6)^{18} & := (68 - 7 + 1 - 9 - 47 + 67 - 3 - 6)^6 \\ & := (68 - 7 + 19 + 4 - 7 - 6 - 73 + 6)^{18} & := (-68 + 7 - 1 + 9 + 47 + 67 - 3 + 6)^6 \\ & := (68 - 7 + 19 - 4 - 7 + 6 - 73 + 6)^{12} & := (68 - 7 + 1 + 9 - 4 + 76 - 73 - 6)^6 \\ & := (68 - 7 + 19 + 4 - 7 + 6 - 73 + 6)^9 & := (68 - 7 - 1 + 9 + 4 - 76 + 73 - 6)^6 \\ & := (-68 + 7 - 19 + 4 + 7 - 6 + 73 + 6)^{18} & := (-68 - 7 + 1 - 9 + 4 + 76 + 73 - 6)^6 \\ & := (-68 + 7 - 19 + 4 - 7 + 6 + 73 + 6)^{36} & := (68 - 7 - 1 - 9 + 4 + 76 - 73 + 6)^6 \\ & := (-68 + 7 - 19 - 4 + 7 + 6 + 73 + 6)^{12} & := (68 + 7 - 1 - 9 - 4 - 76 + 73 + 6)^6 \\ & := (-68 - 7 - 19 + 4 + 7 + 6 + 73 + 6)^{36} & := (68 - 7 + 1 - 9 - 4 - 76 - 7 + 36)^{36} \\ & := (-68 + 7 - 19 + 4 + 7 + 6 + 73 + 6)^9 & := (68 + 7 + 1 - 9 - 4 - 76 - 7 + 36)^9 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} & := (68 - 7 - 1 - 9 + 4 - 76 - 7 + 36)^{12} & := (6 + 87 - 1 - 94 + 76 - 7 + 3 - 6)^6 \\ & := (-68 - 7 - 1 - 9 - 4 + 76 - 7 + 36)^9 & := (-6 + 87 - 1 - 94 + 76 - 7 + 3 + 6)^6 \\ & := (68 - 7 + 1 - 9 - 4 - 76 + 7 + 36)^9 & := (6 + 87 - 1 - 94 - 7 + 6 + 73 - 6)^6 \\ & := (-68 + 7 + 1 + 9 - 4 + 76 + 7 + 36)^6 & := (6 + 87 - 1 - 94 - 7 - 6 + 73 + 6)^6 \\ & := (-6 + 87 + 19 - 4 - 76 - 7 - 3 - 6)^{18} & := (-6 + 87 - 1 - 94 - 7 + 6 + 73 + 6)^6 \\ & := (6 + 87 + 19 - 4 - 76 - 7 - 3 - 6)^9 & := (-6 + 87 - 1 - 94 - 7 - 6 - 7 + 36)^{36} \\ & := (6 - 87 + 19 + 4 + 76 - 7 - 3 - 6)^{36} & := (-6 + 87 + 1 - 94 - 7 - 6 - 7 + 36)^{18} \\ & := (6 - 87 + 19 - 4 + 76 + 7 - 3 - 6)^{12} & := (6 + 87 + 1 - 94 - 7 - 6 - 7 + 36)^9 \\ & := (-6 - 87 + 19 + 4 + 76 + 7 - 3 - 6)^{18} & := (-6 - 87 - 1 + 94 - 7 - 6 - 7 + 36)^9 \\ & := (6 - 87 + 19 + 4 + 76 + 7 - 3 - 6)^9 & := (-6 + 87 - 1 - 94 + 7 - 6 - 7 + 36)^9 \\ & := (6 - 87 + 19 + 4 + 76 - 7 + 3 - 6)^{12} & := (-6 + 87 + 1 - 94 - 7 + 6 - 7 + 36)^9 \\ & := (-6 - 87 + 19 - 4 + 76 + 7 + 3 - 6)^{36} & := (-6 + 87 - 1 - 94 - 7 - 6 + 7 + 36)^9 \\ & := (-6 + 87 + 19 - 4 - 76 - 7 - 3 + 6)^9 & := (-6 - 87 - 1 - 9 + 47 + 67 - 3 - 6)^{36} \\ & := (-6 - 87 + 19 + 4 + 76 - 7 - 3 + 6)^{36} & := (-6 - 87 + 1 - 9 + 47 + 67 - 3 - 6)^{18} \\ & := (6 + 87 - 19 - 4 - 76 + 7 - 3 + 6)^{18} & := (6 - 87 + 1 - 9 + 47 + 67 - 3 - 6)^9 \\ & := (-6 - 87 + 19 - 4 + 76 + 7 - 3 + 6)^{12} & := (-6 - 87 - 1 - 9 + 47 + 67 + 3 - 6)^{12} \\ & := (-6 - 87 + 19 + 4 + 76 + 7 - 3 + 6)^9 & := (-6 - 87 + 1 - 9 + 47 + 67 - 3 + 6)^9 \\ & := (6 + 87 - 19 + 4 - 76 - 7 + 3 + 6)^{18} & := (-6 + 87 - 1 - 9 - 4 + 76 - 73 - 6)^6 \\ & := (-6 - 87 + 19 + 4 + 76 - 7 + 3 + 6)^{12} & := (-6 - 87 + 1 + 9 + 4 + 76 + 73 - 6)^6 \\ & := (-6 + 87 + 19 - 4 - 7 - 6 - 73 - 6)^{18} & := (6 + 87 + 1 + 9 + 4 - 76 + 7 - 36)^{36} \\ & := (6 + 87 + 19 - 4 - 7 - 6 - 73 - 6)^9 & := (-6 - 87 - 1 + 9 - 4 + 76 - 7 + 36)^9 \\ & := (-6 + 87 + 19 - 4 - 7 + 6 - 73 - 6)^9 & := (-6 - 87 + 1 - 9 + 4 + 76 - 7 + 36)^{12} \\ & := (6 + 87 - 19 - 4 + 7 + 6 - 73 - 6)^{18} & := (6 + 87 - 1 + 9 - 4 - 76 + 7 + 36)^6 \\ & := (6 - 87 + 19 - 4 + 7 - 6 + 73 - 6)^{36} & := (6 - 8 + 71 + 9 + 47 + 6 - 73 + 6)^6 \\ & := (6 - 87 + 19 + 4 - 7 + 6 + 73 - 6)^{12} & := (-6 - 8 + 71 + 9 + 47 - 6 - 7 - 36)^6 \\ & := (-6 - 87 + 19 - 4 + 7 + 6 + 73 - 6)^{36} & := (6 - 8 + 71 + 9 - 47 + 6 + 7 - 36)^{12} \\ & := (-6 + 87 + 19 - 4 - 7 - 6 - 73 + 6)^9 & := (6 + 8 - 71 - 9 + 47 - 6 - 7 + 36)^{18} \\ & := (6 + 87 - 19 - 4 + 7 - 6 - 73 + 6)^{18} & := (6 + 8 + 71 - 9 - 47 + 6 - 7 + 36)^6 \\ & := (6 + 87 - 19 - 4 - 7 + 6 - 73 + 6)^{36} & := (-6 + 8 - 71 - 9 + 47 + 6 - 7 + 36)^{18} \\ & := (-6 + 87 - 19 - 4 + 7 + 6 - 73 + 6)^{18} & := (6 + 8 - 71 - 9 + 47 + 6 - 7 + 36)^9 \\ & := (6 + 87 - 19 - 4 + 7 + 6 - 73 + 6)^9 & := (6 - 8 - 71 - 9 + 47 - 6 + 7 + 36)^{36} \\ & := (6 - 87 + 19 + 4 - 7 - 6 + 73 + 6)^{12} & := (-6 - 8 - 71 + 9 + 47 - 6 + 7 + 36)^{12} \\ & := (-6 - 87 + 19 - 4 + 7 - 6 + 73 + 6)^{36} & := (-6 - 8 - 71 - 9 + 47 + 6 + 7 + 36)^{36} \\ & := (-6 - 87 + 19 + 4 - 7 + 6 + 73 + 6)^{12} & := (6 + 8 + 71 + 9 + 4 + 7 - 67 - 36)^{36} \\ & := (-6 + 87 - 19 - 4 - 7 - 6 - 7 - 36)^{36} & := (-6 - 8 - 71 + 9 - 4 - 7 + 67 + 36)^9 \\ & := (-6 + 87 - 19 - 4 + 7 - 6 - 7 - 36)^9 & := (6 + 8 + 7 + 19 + 476 - 7 - 3 + 6)^4 \\ & := (6 + 87 + 19 - 4 - 7 + 6 - 7 - 36)^6 & := (6 + 8 - 7 + 19 + 476 + 7 - 3 + 6)^4 \\ & := (-6 + 87 - 19 - 4 - 7 - 6 + 7 - 36)^9 & := (6 + 8 + 7 + 19 + 47 - 6 - 73 - 6)^{36} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} & := (-6+8+7+19+47+6-73-6)^{36} & := (-6+8+7+1+94+7-67-36)^{12} \\ & := (6+8-7-19-47-6+73-6)^{36} & := (-6+8+7-1+94-7-67+36)^6 \\ & := (-6+8+7-19-47-6+73-6)^{18} & := (6+8-7+1+94-7-67+36)^6 \\ & := (6+8+7-19-47-6+73-6)^9 & := (-6+8-7-1+94+7-67+36)^6 \\ & := (-6+8-7-19-47+6+73-6)^{36} & := (-6-8+7+1+94+7-67+36)^6 \\ & := (-6+8+7-19-47+6+73-6)^9 & := (6+8-7-1-94-7+67+36)^{12} \\ & := (-6+8+7+19+47-6-73+6)^{36} & := (6-8+7+1-94-7+67+36)^{12} \\ & := (-6+8-7-19-47-6+73+6)^{36} & := (-6-8+7-1-94+7+67+36)^{12} \\ & := (-6+8+7-19-47-6+73+6)^9 & := (6-8-7+1-94+7+67+36)^{12} \\ & := (6+8-7+19-47+6+73+6)^6 & := (-6-8-7-1-9+476+73-6)^4 \\ & := (6-8-7+19+47-6-7-36)^{12} & := (687-1-94-76-7-3+6)^4 \\ & := (-6-8-7+19+47+6-7-36)^{12} & := (687-1-94-7+6-73-6)^4 \\ & := (-6+8+7-19+47-6+7-36)^{36} & := (687-1-94-7-6-73+6)^4 \\ & := (6+8+7+19+47+6+7-36)^6 & := (-687+1+9+4+7-6+736)^6 \\ & := (6+8-7+19-47-6-7+36)^{36} & := (68-71+94-7-67-3-6)^{12} \\ & := (-6+8+7+19-47-6-7+36)^{18} & := (68+71+9-47-6-73-6)^9 \\ & := (6+8+7+19-47-6-7+36)^9 & := (68-71-9-47-6+73-6)^{36} \\ & := (-6+8-7+19-47+6-7+36)^{36} & := (-68+71-9-47-6+73-6)^{12} \\ & := (-6+8+7+19-47+6-7+36)^9 & := (-68-71+9+47+6+73+6)^{36} \\ & := (-6+8-7+19-47-6+7+36)^{18} & := (68-71+9+47-6-7-36)^{18} \\ & := (6+8-7+19-47-6+7+36)^9 & := (68+71+9-47+6-7-36)^6 \\ & := (-6-8+7+19-47-6+7+36)^{36} & := (-68+71-9+47+6-7-36)^{18} \\ & := (6+8+7-19-47+6+7+36)^{18} & := (68-71+9+47+6-7-36)^9 \\ & := (-6+8-7+19-47+6+7+36)^9 & := (-68+71-9+47-6-7+36)^6 \\ & := (6+8-7-19-4-7+67-36)^{12} & := (-68+71+9-47-6+7+36)^{36} \\ & := (-6+8-7-19+4-7+67-36)^{18} & := (68-71+9-47+6+7+36)^{12} \\ & := (6+8-7-19+4-7+67-36)^9 & := (68+71-9-4-7-67-36)^9 \\ & := (-6-8+7-19+4-7+67-36)^{36} & := (68-71-9-4-7+67-36)^{12} \\ & := (-6-8+7-19-4+7+67-36)^{12} & := (68-71-9+4-7+67-36)^9 \\ & := (-6-8-7-19+4+7+67-36)^{36} & := (-68+7+194+7-67-3-6)^6 \\ & := (-6-8+7-19+4+7+67-36)^9 & := (68-7-19+47-6-73-6)^{18} \\ & := (6-8+7+19+4+7-67+36)^{18} & := (68-7-19+47+6-73-6)^9 \\ & := (-6+8+7+19+4+7-67+36)^{12} & := (-68-7+19+47+6+73-6)^6 \\ & := (6-8-7-19-4-7+67+36)^6 & := (68-7-19+47-6-73+6)^9 \\ & := (6+8+7-1+94-7-67-36)^{18} & := (-68-7+19+47-6+73+6)^6 \\ & := (6+8-7-1+94+7-67-36)^{18} & := (-68+7-19+47+6-7+36)^{36} \\ & := (6-8+7-1+94+7-67-36)^{36} & := (-68+7-19+47-6+7+36)^{18} \\ & := (6-8+7+1+94+7-67-36)^{18} & := (-68-7-19+47+6+7+36)^{36} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} & := (-68 + 7 - 19 + 47 + 6 + 7 + 36)^9 \\ & := (68 + 7 + 19 + 4 + 7 - 67 - 36)^{36} \\ & := (68 - 7 - 19 + 4 - 7 - 67 + 36)^{12} \\ & := (-68 + 7 + 19 - 4 + 7 + 67 + 36)^6 \\ & := (68 + 7 - 1 - 94 - 7 + 67 - 36)^{18} \\ & := (68 - 7 - 1 - 94 + 7 + 67 - 36)^{18} \\ & := (-68 + 7 - 1 + 94 + 7 - 67 + 36)^{12} \\ & := (68 - 7 + 1 - 94 - 7 + 67 + 36)^6 \\ & := (68 + 7 - 1 - 9 + 476 + 7 - 36)^4 \\ & := (6 - 87 - 19 + 47 - 6 + 73 - 6)^{12} \\ & := (-6 - 87 - 19 + 47 + 6 + 73 - 6)^{12} \\ & := (6 + 87 + 19 - 47 + 6 - 73 + 6)^{18} \\ & := (-6 - 87 - 19 + 47 - 6 + 73 + 6)^{12} \\ & := (-6 + 87 + 19 - 47 - 6 - 7 - 36)^{18} \\ & := (6 + 87 + 19 - 47 - 6 - 7 - 36)^9 \\ & := (-6 + 87 + 19 - 47 + 6 - 7 - 36)^9 \\ & := (6 + 87 - 19 - 47 + 6 + 7 - 36)^{18} \\ & := (6 - 87 + 19 + 47 - 6 - 7 + 36)^{12} \\ & := (-6 - 87 + 19 + 47 + 6 - 7 + 36)^{12} \\ & := (6 + 87 - 19 - 47 - 6 + 7 + 36)^6 \\ & := (-6 + 87 - 19 - 47 + 6 + 7 + 36)^6 \\ & := (-6 + 87 + 19 + 4 + 7 - 67 - 36)^{12} \\ & := (-6 - 87 - 19 + 4 + 7 + 67 + 36)^{36} \\ & := (6 - 87 + 1 - 94 + 7 + 673 + 6)^4 \\ & := (-6 + 87 - 1 + 94 - 7 - 67 - 36)^6 \\ & := (6 + 87 + 1 + 9 + 476 - 73 + 6)^4 \\ & := (6 + 8 + 719 + 4 + 7 - 6 - 736)^{36} \\ & := (-6 + 8 + 719 + 4 + 7 + 6 - 736)^{36} \\ & := (-6 + 8 - 719 - 4 - 7 - 6 + 736)^{36} \\ & := (-6 + 8 - 719 - 4 + 7 - 6 + 736)^9 \\ & := (-6 - 8 - 719 + 4 + 7 - 6 + 736)^{12} \\ & := (6 - 8 + 71 + 94 - 76 - 73 - 6)^{12} \\ & := (-6 + 8 - 71 + 94 - 76 + 73 - 6)^9 \\ & := (-6 - 8 + 71 + 94 - 76 - 73 + 6)^{12} \\ & := (6 + 8 - 71 - 94 + 76 + 73 + 6)^{18} \\ & := (6 - 8 + 71 - 94 + 76 - 7 - 36)^{12} \\ & := (6 + 8 - 71 + 94 - 76 + 7 + 36)^{18} \\ & := (6 - 8 + 71 - 9 + 47 - 67 - 36)^{18} \end{aligned}$$
$$\begin{aligned} & := (-6 + 8 + 71 - 9 + 47 - 67 - 36)^{12} \\ & := (-6 - 8 - 71 + 9 + 47 + 67 - 36)^{36} \\ & := (-6 + 8 + 71 + 9 - 47 - 67 + 36)^{18} \\ & := (6 + 8 + 71 + 9 - 47 - 67 + 36)^9 \\ & := (-6 - 8 + 71 - 9 + 47 - 67 + 36)^6 \\ & := (6 + 8 - 71 + 9 - 47 + 67 + 36)^{12} \\ & := (6 - 8 + 7 + 19 - 47 + 67 - 36)^{12} \\ & := (6 - 8 + 7 - 19 + 47 + 67 - 36)^6 \\ & := (6 + 8 - 7 - 19 + 47 - 67 + 36)^{18} \\ & := (6 - 8 + 7 - 19 + 47 - 67 + 36)^{36} \\ & := (-6 - 8 - 7 - 19 - 47 + 67 + 36)^9 \\ & := (687 + 19 - 4 - 7 - 673 - 6)^9 \\ & := (-687 + 19 - 4 + 7 + 673 - 6)^{36} \\ & := (687 - 19 - 4 + 7 - 673 + 6)^{18} \\ & := (-687 + 19 + 4 - 7 + 673 + 6)^{12} \\ & := (687 - 1 + 94 - 767 - 3 - 6)^{18} \\ & := (687 - 1 + 94 - 767 - 3 + 6)^9 \\ & := (687 + 1 + 9 + 47 - 6 - 736)^{36} \\ & := (-687 - 1 + 9 - 47 - 6 + 736)^{18} \\ & := (-687 - 1 + 9 - 47 + 6 + 736)^9 \\ & := (-68 + 719 + 4 - 76 - 73 + 6)^4 \\ & := (-68 + 71 - 94 + 76 + 73 + 6)^6 \\ & := (-68 - 71 + 94 + 76 + 7 - 36)^{36} \\ & := (68 - 71 - 94 + 76 - 7 + 36)^{12} \\ & := (-68 + 71 + 94 - 76 + 7 + 36)^6 \\ & := (68 - 71 - 9 + 47 - 67 + 36)^{18} \\ & := (-68 - 71 - 9 + 47 + 67 + 36)^{36} \\ & := (68 - 7 + 19 - 47 + 67 - 36)^6 \\ & := (68 - 7 + 19 - 47 - 67 + 36)^{36} \\ & := (68 + 7 + 19 - 47 - 67 + 36)^9 \\ & := (6 - 87 + 194 - 76 + 7 - 36)^{12} \\ & := (6 + 87 - 194 + 76 - 7 + 36)^{18} \\ & := (-6 - 87 + 19 + 47 + 67 - 36)^{18} \\ & := (6 - 87 + 19 + 47 + 67 - 36)^9 \\ & := (-6 - 8 - 719 + 4 + 767 - 36)^{36} \\ & := (-687 + 19 + 4767 + 3 - 6)^3 \\ & := (-687 - 19 + 47 + 673 - 6)^{12} \\ & := (687 - 19 - 4 + 76 - 736)^{18} \end{aligned}$$

$$:= (-68 - 719 + 47 + 6 + 736)^{36}$$

69072400727 := (6 + 90 + 7 + 2 + 4007 - 2 - 7)³
:= (6 + 90 + 7 - 2 + 4007 + 2 - 7)³
:= (6 + 90 - 7 + 2 + 4007 - 2 + 7)³
:= (6 + 90 - 7 - 2 + 4007 + 2 + 7)³
:= (6 + 9 + 072 + 4007 + 2 + 7)³
:= (6 - 9 + 072 + 4007 + 27)³

69173457625 := (6 + 9 + 1 + 7 + 3457 + 625)³

69224023016 := (-6 + 92 + 2 + 4023 + 01 - 6)³

69257922561 := (6 - 9 - 25 - 7 - 9 - 2 - 2 + 561)⁴
:= (6 - 9 - 2 + 579 - 2 - 2 - 56 - 1)⁴
:= (-6 - 9 + 2 + 579 + 2 + 2 - 56 - 1)⁴
:= (6 - 9 - 2 - 5 - 7 - 9 - 22 + 561)⁴
:= (-69 + 2 - 5 - 7 + 9 + 22 + 561)⁴
:= (6 - 92 + 579 + 22 + 5 - 6 - 1)⁴
:= (-6 - 92 + 579 + 22 + 5 + 6 - 1)⁴
:= (6 - 92 + 579 + 2 + 25 - 6 - 1)⁴
:= (-6 - 92 + 579 + 2 + 25 + 6 - 1)⁴
:= (6 + 9 + 257 + 9 + 225 + 6 + 1)⁴
:= (6 + 9 - 25 - 7 - 9 - 22 + 561)⁴
:= (6 - 9 - 25 - 7 + 9 - 22 + 561)⁴
:= (6 + 9 - 2 + 579 - 22 - 56 - 1)⁴
:= (-6 - 9 - 2 - 5 + 792 - 256 - 1)⁴
:= (692 - 57 - 92 - 25 - 6 + 1)⁴
:= (692 - 5 + 79 + 2 - 256 + 1)⁴
:= (-6 + 9 - 25 + 792 - 256 - 1)⁴
:= (6 + 92 + 579 - 225 + 61)⁴

69426531000 := (-6 + 9426 - 5310 + 00)³

69799526416 := (6 + 97 - 9 - 9 + 5 + 2 + 6 + 416)⁴
:= (6 + 9 + 79 - 9 + 5 + 2 + 6 + 416)⁴
:= (6 - 9 + 79 + 9 + 5 + 2 + 6 + 416)⁴
:= (6 + 9 - 7 + 99 - 5 + 2 - 6 + 416)⁴
:= (6 - 9 - 7 + 99 + 5 - 2 + 6 + 416)⁴
:= (-6 + 9 - 7 + 99 - 5 + 2 + 6 + 416)⁴
:= (6 + 9 - 7 - 9 + 95 - 2 + 6 + 416)⁴
:= (6 - 9 - 7 + 9 + 95 - 2 + 6 + 416)⁴
:= (6 - 9 + 7 - 9 + 95 + 2 + 6 + 416)⁴
:= (6 + 9 - 7 + 9 - 9 + 526 - 4 - 16)⁴

$$:= (6 + 9 - 7 - 9 + 9 + 526 - 4 - 16)^4$$

$$:= (6 - 9 - 7 + 9 + 9 + 526 - 4 - 16)^4$$

$$:= (6 + 9 + 7 + 9 + 9 + 52 + 6 + 416)^4$$

$$:= (69 - 79 + 9 + 526 - 4 - 1 - 6)^4$$

$$:= (69 + 7 - 99 + 526 + 4 + 1 + 6)^4$$

$$:= (6 - 9 + 79 - 9 + 5 + 26 + 416)^4$$

$$:= (-6 - 9 - 7 + 99 - 5 + 26 + 416)^4$$

$$:= (697 - 9 + 95 - 264 + 1 - 6)^4$$

$$:= (69 + 79 + 95 + 264 + 1 + 6)^4$$

$$:= (-69 - 7 + 99 + 526 - 41 + 6)^4$$

$$:= (6 + 979 - 9 - 52 + 6 - 416)^4$$

$$:= (6 - 97 + 99 + 526 - 4 - 16)^4$$

$$:= (6 - 97 + 995 + 26 - 416)^4$$

69985463561 := (6 + 9 - 9 + 8 + 546 + 3561)³
:= (6 - 9 + 9 + 8 + 546 + 3561)³

70087408867 := (7 + 008 + 7 + 4088 + 6 + 7)³

70138418624 := (-70 - 1 + 3 + 8 + 4186 + 2 - 4)³
:= (-70 + 1 - 3 + 8 + 4186 - 2 + 4)³
:= (70 - 138 + 4186 + 2 + 4)³

70344300625 := (70 + 3 + 443 + 006 - 2 - 5)⁴
:= (70 + 34 + 430 + 06 - 25)⁴

70393838689 := (70 + 3938 + 38 - 6 + 89)³

70803799353 := (-7 - 08 + 03799 + 353)³

70892257536 := (-7 + 08 - 9 + 2 - 2 - 5 - 7 + 536)⁴
:= (-7 + 08 - 9 - 2 + 2 - 5 - 7 + 536)⁴
:= (7 - 08 - 9 - 22 + 5 + 7 + 536)⁴
:= (-7 + 08 + 9 + 2 - 25 - 7 + 536)⁴
:= (70 - 8 - 92 - 2 + 5 + 7 + 536)⁴
:= (7 - 08 - 92 - 2 + 575 + 36)⁴
:= (-7 - 08 + 9 - 225 + 753 - 6)⁴
:= (708 - 92 - 2 - 57 - 5 - 36)⁴
:= (708 + 9 - 225 - 7 - 5 + 36)⁴
:= (70 - 89 - 2 - 2 + 575 - 36)⁴

71008211968 := (71 + 0082 + 1 - 1 + 9 - 6 - 8)⁵
:= (71 + 0082 - 1 + 1 + 9 - 6 - 8)⁵
:= (71 + 0082 + 1 + 1 - 9 - 6 + 8)⁵
:= (7 + 100 + 8 + 21 + 1 + 9 - 6 + 8)⁵
:= (-7 + 100 - 8 + 2 + 1 + 1 - 9 + 68)⁵

$$\begin{aligned}
 &:= (7 + 10 + 08 + 2 + 119 - 6 + 8)^5 \\
 &:= (7 - 1 + 008 + 211 - 9 - 68)^5 \\
 &:= (7 + 10 + 08 + 211 - 96 + 8)^5 \\
 &:= (7 + 100 - 8 - 2 + 119 - 68)^5 \\
 \mathbf{71266904136} &:= (7 + 12 + 6 - 6 - 9 + 04136)^3 \\
 &:= (7 + 12 - 6 + 6 - 9 + 04136)^3 \\
 &:= (71 + 2 + 6 - 69 + 04136)^3 \\
 \mathbf{71421719949} &:= (-71 + 4217 - 19 + 9 + 4 + 9)^3 \\
 \mathbf{71443409521} &:= (7 - 1 + 4 - 4 + 3 - 4 - 09 + 521)^4 \\
 &:= (7 - 1 - 4 + 4 + 3 - 4 - 09 + 521)^4 \\
 &:= (7 - 1 - 4 - 4 + 3 + 4 - 09 + 521)^4 \\
 &:= (-7 + 1 + 4 - 4 - 3 - 4 + 09 + 521)^4 \\
 &:= (-7 + 1 - 4 + 4 - 3 - 4 + 09 + 521)^4 \\
 &:= (-7 + 1 - 4 - 4 - 3 + 4 + 09 + 521)^4 \\
 &:= (71 + 443 - 4 + 09 - 5 + 2 + 1)^4 \\
 &:= (71 + 443 + 4 - 09 + 5 + 2 + 1)^4 \\
 &:= (7 + 1 + 443 + 4 + 09 + 52 + 1)^4 \\
 &:= (71 + 443 - 4 - 09 - 5 + 21)^4 \\
 &:= (71 + 44 - 3 + 409 - 5 + 2 - 1)^4 \\
 &:= (71 - 4 + 43 + 409 - 5 + 2 + 1)^4 \\
 &:= (71 + 4 + 4 + 340 + 95 + 2 + 1)^4 \\
 &:= (71 + 4 + 4 + 3 + 409 + 5 + 21)^4 \\
 &:= (7 + 14 + 434 + 09 + 52 + 1)^4 \\
 &:= (-7 - 1 + 443 + 40 - 9 + 52 - 1)^4 \\
 &:= (7 + 1 + 44 + 3 + 409 + 52 + 1)^4 \\
 &:= (7 - 1 - 44 + 3 + 40 - 9 + 521)^4 \\
 &:= (-7 + 1 - 44 - 3 + 40 + 9 + 521)^4 \\
 &:= (-7 + 1 + 4 - 434 + 0952 + 1)^4 \\
 &:= (7 + 1 + 4 + 43 + 409 + 52 + 1)^4 \\
 &:= (7 - 1 - 4 + 43 - 40 - 9 + 521)^4 \\
 &:= (-7 + 1 - 4 - 43 + 40 + 9 + 521)^4 \\
 &:= (71 + 44 + 340 + 9 + 52 + 1)^4 \\
 &:= (-7 + 144 - 3 + 409 - 5 - 21)^4 \\
 \mathbf{71939391679} &:= (71 - 9 + 3939 + 167 - 9)^3 \\
 \mathbf{71997768976} &:= (-71 - 99 + 7 - 7 + 689 - 7 + 6)^4 \\
 &:= (-71 - 99 - 7 + 7 + 689 - 7 + 6)^4 \\
 &:= (-71 - 99 - 7 - 7 + 689 + 7 + 6)^4 \\
 &:= (-71 - 9 - 97 + 7 + 689 - 7 + 6)^4
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 &:= (-71 - 9 - 97 - 7 + 689 + 7 + 6)^4 \\
 &:= (7 - 1 - 99 - 77 + 689 - 7 + 6)^4 \\
 &:= (-7 - 1 - 99 - 77 + 689 + 7 + 6)^4 \\
 &:= (-71 - 99 + 776 - 89 + 7 - 6)^4 \\
 &:= (-71 + 9 - 97 + 768 - 97 + 6)^4 \\
 &:= (7 - 1 - 99 + 776 - 89 - 76)^4 \\
 &:= (719 - 9 + 776 + 8 - 976)^4 \\
 &:= (-71 - 99 - 77 + 689 + 76)^4 \\
 \mathbf{72162614161} &:= (7216 + 261416 - 1)^2 \\
 \mathbf{72407429632} &:= (72 + 4074 + 2 + 9 + 6 + 3 + 2)^3 \\
 &:= (7 - 2 + 4074 - 2 + 96 - 3 - 2)^3 \\
 &:= (-7 + 2 + 4074 + 2 + 96 + 3 - 2)^3 \\
 &:= (-7 + 2 + 4074 - 2 + 96 + 3 + 2)^3 \\
 &:= (-7 - 2 + 4074 + 2 + 96 + 3 + 2)^3 \\
 &:= (72 + 4074 + 29 - 6 - 3 + 2)^3 \\
 \mathbf{72555348321} &:= (7 + 2 - 5 - 5 + 534 - 8 - 3 - 2 - 1)^4 \\
 &:= (7 - 2 - 5 - 5 + 534 - 8 - 3 + 2 - 1)^4 \\
 &:= (-7 + 2 + 5 - 5 + 534 - 8 - 3 + 2 - 1)^4 \\
 &:= (-7 + 2 - 5 + 5 + 534 - 8 - 3 + 2 - 1)^4 \\
 &:= (-7 - 2 - 5 - 5 + 534 + 8 - 3 - 2 + 1)^4 \\
 &:= (-7 - 2 + 5 - 5 + 534 - 8 + 3 - 2 + 1)^4 \\
 &:= (-7 - 2 - 5 + 5 + 534 - 8 + 3 - 2 + 1)^4 \\
 &:= (-7 - 25 + 553 - 4 + 8 - 3 - 2 - 1)^4 \\
 &:= (7 - 25 + 553 - 4 - 8 - 3 - 2 + 1)^4 \\
 &:= (-7 - 25 + 553 + 4 - 8 + 3 - 2 + 1)^4 \\
 &:= (7 - 25 - 5 + 534 + 8 + 3 - 2 - 1)^4 \\
 &:= (-7 - 25 + 5 + 534 + 8 + 3 + 2 - 1)^4 \\
 &:= (7 - 25 - 5 + 534 + 8 - 3 + 2 + 1)^4 \\
 &:= (7 + 25 + 5 + 5 - 3 + 483 - 2 - 1)^4 \\
 &:= (7 + 25 + 5 - 5 + 3 + 483 + 2 - 1)^4 \\
 &:= (7 + 25 - 5 + 5 + 3 + 483 + 2 - 1)^4 \\
 &:= (7 + 2 + 555 + 3 - 48 + 3 - 2 - 1)^4 \\
 &:= (7 - 2 + 555 + 3 - 48 + 3 + 2 - 1)^4 \\
 &:= (7 + 2 + 555 - 3 - 48 + 3 + 2 + 1)^4 \\
 &:= (-7 + 2 + 555 - 3 + 4 - 8 - 3 - 21)^4 \\
 &:= (-7 - 2 + 555 + 3 - 4 - 8 + 3 - 21)^4
 \end{aligned}$$

$:= (7 + 2 + 5 + 553 - 48 + 3 - 2 - 1)^4$	$:= (73 + 4 - 3 + 9 + 77 - 5 + 7 - 4 - 9)^5$
$:= (7 - 2 + 5 + 553 - 48 + 3 + 2 - 1)^4$	$:= (73 + 4 + 3 + 9 + 77 - 5 - 7 + 4 - 9)^5$
$:= (7 + 2 + 5 + 553 - 48 - 3 + 2 + 1)^4$	$:= (73 - 4 - 3 + 9 + 77 - 5 + 7 + 4 - 9)^5$
$:= (-7 - 2 - 5 + 553 - 4 + 8 - 3 - 21)^4$	$:= (73 + 4 - 3 - 9 + 77 + 5 + 7 + 4 - 9)^5$
$:= (-7 - 2 + 5 + 553 - 4 - 8 + 3 - 21)^4$	$:= (73 + 4 - 3 - 9 + 77 - 5 + 7 - 4 + 9)^5$
$:= (-7 - 2 + 5 + 5 + 534 + 8 - 3 - 21)^4$	$:= (73 + 4 + 3 - 9 + 77 - 5 - 7 + 4 + 9)^5$
$:= (7 - 2 - 5 - 5 + 534 + 8 + 3 - 21)^4$	$:= (73 - 4 - 3 - 9 + 77 - 5 + 7 + 4 + 9)^5$
$:= (-7 + 2 + 5 - 5 + 534 + 8 + 3 - 21)^4$	$:= (73 + 4 - 3 - 9 + 7 + 75 + 7 + 4 - 9)^5$
$:= (-7 + 2 - 5 + 5 + 534 + 8 + 3 - 21)^4$	$:= (73 + 4 - 3 + 9 - 7 + 75 - 7 - 4 + 9)^5$
$:= (-72 + 555 + 34 + 8 - 3 - 2 - 1)^4$	$:= (73 - 4 - 3 + 9 - 7 + 75 - 7 + 4 + 9)^5$
$:= (-72 + 55 + 534 + 8 - 3 - 2 - 1)^4$	$:= (73 + 4 - 3 + 9 + 7 + 7 + 57 + 4 - 9)^5$
$:= (-72 - 5 + 553 + 4 + 8 + 32 - 1)^4$	$:= (73 + 4 - 3 - 9 + 7 + 7 + 57 + 4 + 9)^5$
$:= (-7 + 25 + 553 - 48 - 3 - 2 + 1)^4$	$:= (73 + 4 + 3 + 9 + 7 - 7 - 5 + 74 - 9)^5$
$:= (-7 + 25 + 5 - 5 - 3 + 483 + 21)^4$	$:= (73 + 4 + 3 + 9 - 7 + 7 - 5 + 74 - 9)^5$
$:= (-7 + 25 - 5 + 5 - 3 + 483 + 21)^4$	$:= (73 - 4 - 3 + 9 + 7 + 7 - 5 + 74 - 9)^5$
$:= (-7 - 2 + 555 + 3 - 48 - 3 + 21)^4$	$:= (73 + 4 - 3 - 9 + 7 + 7 + 5 + 74 - 9)^5$
$:= (-7 - 2 + 555 - 3 - 48 + 3 + 21)^4$	$:= (73 + 4 + 3 - 9 + 7 - 7 - 5 + 74 + 9)^5$
$:= (-7 - 2 + 5 + 553 - 48 - 3 + 21)^4$	$:= (73 + 4 + 3 - 9 - 7 + 7 - 5 + 74 + 9)^5$
$:= (-7 + 2 - 5 + 553 - 48 + 3 + 21)^4$	$:= (73 - 4 - 3 - 9 + 7 + 7 - 5 + 74 + 9)^5$
$:= (72 - 55 + 534 - 8 - 3 - 21)^4$	$:= (73 - 4 - 3 + 9 - 7 - 7 + 5 + 74 + 9)^5$
$:= (72 - 55 - 5 + 3 + 483 + 21)^4$	$:= (7 + 34 - 3 + 97 + 7 + 5 + 7 + 4 - 9)^5$
$:= (72 - 5 - 55 + 3 + 483 + 21)^4$	$:= (7 + 34 - 3 + 97 + 7 - 5 + 7 - 4 + 9)^5$
$:= (-7 + 255 - 5 + 3 - 48 + 321)^4$	$:= (7 + 34 + 3 + 97 + 7 - 5 - 7 + 4 + 9)^5$
$:= (7 + 25 + 553 - 48 + 3 - 21)^4$	$:= (7 + 34 + 3 + 97 - 7 - 5 + 7 + 4 + 9)^5$
$:= (7 + 25 + 553 - 4 - 83 + 21)^4$	$:= (-7 + 34 + 3 + 97 + 7 - 5 + 7 + 4 + 9)^5$
$:= (-7 - 2 + 555 - 348 + 321)^4$	$:= (7 + 34 - 3 + 9 + 77 + 5 + 7 + 4 + 9)^5$
72695483641 $:= (7 + 269548 + 3 + 64 - 1)^2$	$:= (7 + 34 - 3 + 9 + 7 + 75 + 7 + 4 + 9)^5$
72696562129 $:= (-7 + 269656 + 2 + 1 - 29)^2$	$:= (7 + 34 - 3 + 9 + 7 + 7 + 5 + 74 + 9)^5$
72877493233 $:= (72 + 877 + 4 - 9 + 3233)^3$	$:= (7 - 3 + 4 + 39 + 77 + 5 + 7 + 4 + 9)^5$
73116160000 $:= (-73 + 1 - 1 - 6 - 1 + 600 + 00)^4$	$:= (7 - 3 + 4 + 39 + 7 + 75 + 7 + 4 + 9)^5$
$:= (-73 - 1 + 1 - 6 - 1 + 600 + 00)^4$	$:= (7 - 3 + 4 + 39 + 7 + 7 + 5 + 74 + 9)^5$
$:= (-73 - 1 - 1 - 6 + 1 + 600 + 00)^4$	$:= (7 - 3 - 4 - 3 + 97 + 75 - 7 - 4 - 9)^5$
73191996487 $:= (7 + 3191 + 996 + 4 - 8 - 7)^3$	$:= (-7 + 3 + 4 - 3 + 97 + 75 - 7 - 4 - 9)^5$
$:= (-7 + 3191 + 996 + 4 - 8 + 7)^3$	$:= (-7 - 3 + 4 + 3 + 97 + 75 - 7 - 4 - 9)^5$
73349586856 $:= (7 - 3 + 3495 + 8 + 685 - 6)^3$	$:= (-7 - 3 - 4 - 3 + 97 + 75 + 7 - 4 - 9)^5$
73439775749 $:= (73 + 4 - 3 + 97 - 7 + 5 - 7 - 4 - 9)^5$	$:= (-7 + 3 - 4 - 3 + 97 + 75 - 7 + 4 - 9)^5$
$:= (73 - 4 - 3 + 97 - 7 + 5 - 7 + 4 - 9)^5$	$:= (-7 - 3 - 4 + 3 + 97 + 75 - 7 + 4 - 9)^5$
$:= (73 - 4 - 3 + 97 - 7 - 5 - 7 - 4 + 9)^5$	$:= (7 - 3 - 4 - 3 + 97 - 7 + 57 - 4 + 9)^5$

$:= (-7 + 3 + 4 - 3 + 97 - 7 + 57 - 4 + 9)^5$	$:= (73 - 43 - 9 + 77 - 5 + 7 + 49)^5$
$:= (-7 - 3 + 4 + 3 + 97 - 7 + 57 - 4 + 9)^5$	$:= (73 - 43 + 9 - 7 + 75 - 7 + 49)^5$
$:= (-7 - 3 - 4 - 3 + 97 + 7 + 57 - 4 + 9)^5$	$:= (73 + 4 + 39 + 77 - 57 + 4 + 9)^5$
$:= (-7 + 3 - 4 - 3 + 97 - 7 + 57 + 4 + 9)^5$	$:= (7 + 34 - 39 + 77 + 57 + 4 + 9)^5$
$:= (-7 - 3 - 4 + 3 + 97 - 7 + 57 + 4 + 9)^5$	$:= (7 - 34 + 39 + 77 - 5 + 74 - 9)^5$
$:= (-7 + 3 - 4 - 3 + 97 - 7 + 5 + 74 - 9)^5$	$:= (7 + 34 - 39 + 77 + 5 + 74 - 9)^5$
$:= (-7 - 3 - 4 + 3 + 97 - 7 + 5 + 74 - 9)^5$	$:= (7 + 34 - 39 + 7 + 75 + 74 - 9)^5$
$:= (7 + 3 + 4 - 3 + 9 + 77 + 57 + 4 - 9)^5$	$:= (-7 - 34 + 39 - 7 + 75 + 74 + 9)^5$
$:= (7 - 3 + 4 + 3 + 9 + 77 + 57 + 4 - 9)^5$	$:= (7 + 34 + 3 + 97 - 75 + 74 + 9)^5$
$:= (7 + 3 + 4 - 3 - 9 + 77 + 57 + 4 + 9)^5$	$:= (-7 - 3 + 43 + 97 + 75 - 7 - 49)^5$
$:= (7 - 3 + 4 + 3 - 9 + 77 + 57 + 4 + 9)^5$	$:= (7 + 3 + 43 + 97 + 7 - 57 + 49)^5$
$:= (7 + 3 - 4 - 3 + 9 + 77 - 5 + 74 - 9)^5$	$:= (-7 + 3 - 43 + 97 - 7 + 57 + 49)^5$
$:= (7 - 3 - 4 + 3 + 9 + 77 - 5 + 74 - 9)^5$	$:= (-73 - 4 + 3 + 977 - 5 - 749)^5$
$:= (-7 + 3 + 4 + 3 + 9 + 77 - 5 + 74 - 9)^5$	$:= (7 + 34 + 39 + 77 - 57 + 49)^5$
$:= (7 + 3 + 4 - 3 - 9 + 77 + 5 + 74 - 9)^5$	73665445888 $:= (7 - 366 + 5 + 4458 + 88)^3$
$:= (7 - 3 + 4 + 3 - 9 + 77 + 5 + 74 - 9)^5$	73680216481 $:= (-7 + 36 + 8 - 02 - 1 + 6 + 481)^4$
$:= (7 + 3 - 4 - 3 - 9 + 77 - 5 + 74 + 9)^5$	$:= (7 + 36 - 8 - 02 + 1 + 6 + 481)^4$
$:= (7 - 3 - 4 + 3 - 9 + 77 - 5 + 74 + 9)^5$	$:= (-73 + 680 - 2 - 1 - 6 + 4 - 81)^4$
$:= (-7 + 3 + 4 + 3 - 9 + 77 - 5 + 74 + 9)^5$	$:= (7 + 368 + 02 - 1 + 64 + 81)^4$
$:= (7 + 3 + 4 - 3 - 9 + 7 + 75 + 74 - 9)^5$	$:= (-7 - 36 - 80 - 2 - 1 + 648 - 1)^4$
$:= (7 - 3 + 4 + 3 - 9 + 7 + 75 + 74 - 9)^5$	$:= (-7 - 36 + 80 - 2 - 1 + 6 + 481)^4$
$:= (-7 + 3 - 4 - 3 + 9 - 7 + 75 + 74 + 9)^5$	$:= (-7 + 3 + 680 + 2 - 164 + 8 - 1)^4$
$:= (-7 - 3 - 4 + 3 + 9 - 7 + 75 + 74 + 9)^5$	$:= (7 + 3 + 680 + 2 - 164 - 8 + 1)^4$
$:= (73 - 43 + 97 + 7 - 5 + 7 + 4 + 9)^5$	$:= (-7 - 3 + 68 - 02 - 16 + 481)^4$
$:= (73 + 4 + 39 - 7 - 7 + 5 - 7 + 49)^5$	$:= (-73 + 6 - 80 + 21 + 648 - 1)^4$
$:= (73 - 4 - 3 - 9 - 7 - 7 + 57 + 49)^5$	$:= (-73 + 6 + 80 + 21 + 6 + 481)^4$
$:= (7 + 34 + 3 - 9 + 77 - 5 - 7 + 49)^5$	$:= (7 + 3 + 680 - 216 + 48 - 1)^4$
$:= (-7 + 34 + 3 - 9 + 77 - 5 + 7 + 49)^5$	73770933384 $:= (73 + 770 + 9 + 3338 + 4)^3$
$:= (-7 + 34 + 3 + 9 - 7 + 75 - 7 + 49)^5$	73823714875 $:= (7 + 382 + 3714 + 87 + 5)^3$
$:= (7 + 34 - 3 - 9 + 7 + 7 + 57 + 49)^5$	74140932601 $:= (-7 + 4140 + 93 - 26 + 01)^3$
$:= (7 + 3 - 43 + 97 + 7 - 5 + 74 + 9)^5$	74246873427 $:= (7 + 4246 - 8 - 73 + 4 + 27)^3$
$:= (-7 - 3 - 4 + 39 + 77 + 5 - 7 + 49)^5$	74247530256 $:= (7 + 424 + 75 + 3 + 02 + 5 + 6)^4$
$:= (7 - 3 - 4 + 39 - 7 + 75 - 7 + 49)^5$	$:= (7 + 42 + 475 - 3 + 02 + 5 - 6)^4$
$:= (-7 + 3 + 4 + 39 - 7 + 75 - 7 + 49)^5$	$:= (-7 + 42 + 475 + 3 - 02 + 5 + 6)^4$
$:= (-7 - 3 - 4 + 39 + 7 + 75 - 7 + 49)^5$	$:= (7 + 4 + 2 + 475 + 3 + 025 + 6)^4$
$:= (-7 - 3 - 4 + 39 - 7 + 75 + 7 + 49)^5$	$:= (74 + 2 + 475 - 30 + 2 + 5 - 6)^4$
$:= (734 + 3 + 9 - 7 - 7 - 574 - 9)^5$	$:= (7 + 424 + 75 - 3 + 025 - 6)^4$
$:= (734 + 3 - 9 - 7 - 7 - 574 + 9)^5$	$:= (7 + 424 + 7 + 53 + 025 + 6)^4$

$$\begin{aligned}
 &:= (7 + 42 + 4 - 7 + 530 + 2 - 56)^4 \\
 &:= (-7 + 42 + 4 + 7 + 530 + 2 - 56)^4 \\
 &:= (-7 - 4 + 247 - 5 + 302 - 5 - 6)^4 \\
 &:= (7 + 4 + 247 + 5 + 3 + 0256)^4 \\
 &:= (-7 + 4 + 2 + 47 + 530 + 2 - 56)^4 \\
 &:= (742 - 4 + 75 - 302 + 5 + 6)^4 \\
 &:= (742 + 4 + 7 - 5 + 30 - 256)^4 \\
 \mathbf{74299881664} &:= (7 + 4299 - 88 - 16 + 6 - 4)^3 \\
 \mathbf{74352915125} &:= (-7 + 4352 - 9 - 1 - 5 - 125)^3 \\
 \mathbf{74512166912} &:= (7 + 4 + 5121 - 6 - 6 - 912)^3 \\
 \mathbf{74671645931} &:= (7 + 4671 - 6 - 459 - 3 + 1)^3 \\
 \mathbf{74724856128} &:= (7 + 4724 + 85 - 612 + 8)^3 \\
 \mathbf{74727329769} &:= (74 + 7 + 273297 - 6 - 9)^2 \\
 \mathbf{74818113841} &:= (7 + 481 + 8 + 11 + 3 + 8 + 4 + 1)^4 \\
 &:= (7 + 481 + 8 + 1 + 13 + 8 + 4 + 1)^4 \\
 &:= (-7 + 481 + 8 + 1 - 1 + 38 + 4 - 1)^4 \\
 &:= (-7 + 481 + 8 - 1 + 1 + 38 + 4 - 1)^4 \\
 &:= (7 + 481 - 8 + 1 + 1 + 38 + 4 - 1)^4 \\
 &:= (-7 + 481 + 8 - 1 - 1 + 38 + 4 + 1)^4 \\
 &:= (7 + 481 - 8 + 1 - 1 + 38 + 4 + 1)^4 \\
 &:= (7 + 481 - 8 - 1 + 1 + 38 + 4 + 1)^4 \\
 &:= (-7 + 481 + 81 + 1 - 38 + 4 + 1)^4 \\
 &:= (-7 + 481 + 8 + 11 - 3 - 8 + 41)^4 \\
 &:= (-7 + 481 - 8 + 11 - 3 + 8 + 41)^4 \\
 &:= (-7 + 481 + 8 - 11 + 3 + 8 + 41)^4 \\
 &:= (7 + 48 + 1 + 81 + 1 + 384 + 1)^4 \\
 &:= (748 - 181 - 1 - 38 - 4 - 1)^4 \\
 &:= (748 - 1 - 81 - 138 - 4 - 1)^4 \\
 &:= (7 + 481 + 81 - 13 + 8 - 41)^4 \\
 \mathbf{74884638375} &:= (-7 - 488 + 4638 - 3 + 75)^3 \\
 \mathbf{75044648232} &:= (-7 + 5044 + 6 - 4 - 823 + 2)^3 \\
 \mathbf{75258349048} &:= (-752 - 5 + 83 + 4904 - 8)^3 \\
 \mathbf{75391979776} &:= (-7 + 539 + 1 + 9 - 7 + 9 - 7 - 7 - 6)^4 \\
 &:= (75 + 391 - 9 - 7 - 9 + 77 + 6)^4 \\
 &:= (75 + 391 - 9 + 7 - 9 - 7 + 76)^4 \\
 &:= (75 + 391 - 9 - 7 - 9 + 7 + 76)^4 \\
 &:= (7 + 539 + 1 - 97 - 9 + 77 + 6)^4 \\
 &:= (7 + 539 + 1 - 97 - 9 + 7 + 76)^4
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 &:= (7 + 539 + 1 - 9 + 7 - 97 + 76)^4 \\
 \mathbf{75418890625} &:= (7 + 5 + 41 + 8 + 8 + 9 - 06 - 2 - 5)^6 \\
 &:= (7 + 5 + 41 + 8 - 8 + 9 + 06 + 2 - 5)^6 \\
 &:= (7 + 5 + 41 - 8 + 8 + 9 + 06 + 2 - 5)^6 \\
 &:= (7 - 5 + 41 + 8 + 8 + 9 - 06 - 2 + 5)^6 \\
 &:= (-7 + 5 + 41 + 8 + 8 + 9 - 06 + 2 + 5)^6 \\
 &:= (7 - 5 + 41 + 8 - 8 + 9 + 06 + 2 + 5)^6 \\
 &:= (7 - 5 + 41 - 8 + 8 + 9 + 06 + 2 + 5)^6 \\
 &:= (7 - 5 - 4 + 1 + 88 - 9 - 06 - 2 - 5)^6 \\
 &:= (-7 + 5 - 4 + 1 + 88 - 9 - 06 + 2 - 5)^6 \\
 &:= (-7 - 5 - 4 - 1 + 88 - 9 + 06 + 2 - 5)^6 \\
 &:= (-7 - 5 - 4 + 1 + 88 - 9 - 06 + 2 + 5)^6 \\
 &:= (7 - 5 - 4 - 1 - 8 + 89 - 06 - 2 - 5)^6 \\
 &:= (-7 + 5 - 4 - 1 - 8 + 89 - 06 + 2 - 5)^6 \\
 &:= (-7 - 5 + 4 + 1 - 8 + 89 - 06 + 2 - 5)^6 \\
 &:= (-7 - 5 - 4 - 1 - 8 + 89 - 06 + 2 + 5)^6 \\
 &:= (7 + 5 + 4 + 1 + 8 - 8 - 9 + 062 - 5)^6 \\
 &:= (7 + 5 + 4 + 1 - 8 + 8 - 9 + 062 - 5)^6 \\
 &:= (-7 + 5 + 4 - 1 + 8 + 8 - 9 + 062 - 5)^6 \\
 &:= (7 + 5 + 4 - 1 - 8 - 8 + 9 + 062 - 5)^6 \\
 &:= (7 - 5 - 4 + 1 + 8 - 8 + 9 + 062 - 5)^6 \\
 &:= (7 - 5 - 4 + 1 - 8 + 8 + 9 + 062 - 5)^6 \\
 &:= (-7 - 5 - 4 - 1 + 8 + 8 + 9 + 062 - 5)^6 \\
 &:= (7 + 5 - 4 - 1 + 8 - 8 - 9 + 062 + 5)^6 \\
 &:= (7 - 5 + 4 + 1 + 8 - 8 - 9 + 062 + 5)^6 \\
 &:= (7 - 5 + 4 + 1 - 8 + 8 - 9 + 062 + 5)^6 \\
 &:= (-7 - 5 + 4 - 1 + 8 + 8 - 9 + 062 + 5)^6 \\
 &:= (7 - 5 + 4 - 1 - 8 - 8 + 9 + 062 + 5)^6 \\
 &:= (7 + 5 - 4 + 1 + 8 + 8 + 9 + 06 + 25)^6 \\
 &:= (75 + 4 - 18 + 8 + 9 - 06 - 2 - 5)^6 \\
 &:= (75 + 4 - 18 - 8 + 9 + 06 + 2 - 5)^6 \\
 &:= (75 - 4 - 18 + 8 - 9 + 06 + 2 + 5)^6 \\
 &:= (7 + 54 + 18 + 8 - 9 - 06 - 2 - 5)^6 \\
 &:= (-7 + 54 + 18 - 8 + 9 + 06 - 2 - 5)^6 \\
 &:= (7 + 54 + 18 - 8 - 9 + 06 + 2 - 5)^6 \\
 &:= (-7 + 54 + 18 + 8 - 9 - 06 + 2 + 5)^6
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 &:= (7 + 5 - 41 + 88 + 9 - 06 - 2 + 5)^6 & &:= (-7 - 5 - 4 + 18 - 8 + 90 + 6 - 25)^6 \\
 &:= (7 + 5 - 41 + 8 + 89 - 06 - 2 + 5)^6 & &:= (-75 - 41 + 88 + 90 + 6 + 2 - 5)^6 \\
 &:= (7 + 5 - 41 - 8 + 89 + 06 + 2 + 5)^6 & &:= (75 + 4 + 18 - 89 + 062 - 5)^6 \\
 &:= (-7 + 5 + 41 + 8 + 8 - 9 - 06 + 25)^6 & &:= (7 - 54 + 188 - 9 - 062 - 5)^6 \\
 &:= (7 + 5 + 41 - 8 - 8 + 9 - 06 + 25)^6 & &:= (7 + 54 - 18 + 89 - 062 - 5)^6 \\
 &:= (7 - 5 + 41 + 8 - 8 - 9 + 06 + 25)^6 & &:= (-7 - 54 + 18 + 89 - 06 + 25)^6 \\
 &:= (7 - 5 + 41 - 8 + 8 - 9 + 06 + 25)^6 & &:= (7 - 54 + 1 + 88 + 90 - 62 - 5)^6 \\
 &:= (7 - 5 - 4 - 18 + 8 + 90 - 6 - 2 - 5)^6 & &:= (-7 + 54 + 1 + 88 - 90 - 6 + 25)^6 \\
 &:= (-7 + 5 + 4 - 18 - 8 + 90 + 6 - 2 - 5)^6 & &:= (7 - 5 - 4 + 188 - 90 - 6 - 25)^6 \\
 &:= (-7 + 5 - 4 - 18 + 8 + 90 - 6 + 2 - 5)^6 & &:= (754 + 18 + 8 - 90 - 625)^6 \\
 &:= (7 - 5 - 4 - 18 - 8 + 90 + 6 + 2 - 5)^6 & &**75633300989** := (-7 - 56 + 3 + 3300 + 989)^3 \\
 &:= (-7 - 5 + 4 - 18 - 8 + 90 + 6 - 2 + 5)^6 & &**75740658391** := (7 + 57 + 4065 + 8 + 3 + 91)^3 \\
 &:= (-7 - 5 - 4 - 18 + 8 + 90 - 6 + 2 + 5)^6 & &**75819274609** := (-75 + 819 + 274609)^2 \\
 &:= (7 + 5 + 4 + 1 + 88 - 9 - 06 - 25)^6 & &**75827535424** := (7 + 5 + 8 + 275354 - 2 - 4)^2 \\
 &:= (7 - 5 - 4 + 1 + 88 + 9 - 06 - 25)^6 & &:= (-7 + 5 - 8 + 275354 + 24)^2 \\
 &:= (7 - 5 + 4 - 1 + 88 - 9 + 06 - 25)^6 & &**75901884904** := (-759 + 01 + 88 + 4904)^3 \\
 &:= (7 + 5 + 4 - 1 - 8 + 89 - 06 - 25)^6 & &:= (7 - 590 + 1 - 88 + 4904)^3 \\
 &:= (7 - 5 - 4 + 1 + 8 + 89 - 06 - 25)^6 & &**75937500000** := (-7 - 593 + 750 + 0000)^5 \\
 &:= (-7 + 5 + 4 + 1 - 8 + 89 + 06 - 25)^6 & &**75969140625** := (7 + 596 - 91 + 4 + 06 - 2 + 5)^4 \\
 &:= (-75 + 41 + 8 - 8 + 90 + 6 - 2 + 5)^6 & &:= (7 + 5 + 96 + 9 - 1 + 406 - 2 + 5)^4 \\
 &:= (-75 + 41 - 8 + 8 + 90 + 6 - 2 + 5)^6 & &:= (7 - 5 - 96 - 9 - 1 + 4 + 0625)^4 \\
 &:= (75 + 4 + 18 + 8 - 9 - 06 - 25)^6 & &:= (-7 + 5 - 9 + 6 - 91 - 4 + 0625)^4 \\
 &:= (75 + 4 + 1 + 88 - 90 - 6 - 2 - 5)^6 & &:= (7 - 5 - 9 - 6 - 91 + 4 + 0625)^4 \\
 &:= (75 - 4 + 1 - 88 + 90 - 6 + 2 - 5)^6 & &:= (-7 + 596 - 91 + 40 - 6 - 2 - 5)^4 \\
 &:= (75 - 4 - 1 + 88 - 90 - 6 - 2 + 5)^6 & &:= (-7 + 596 - 91 - 4 + 06 + 25)^4 \\
 &:= (75 - 4 + 1 + 8 + 8 - 90 + 62 + 5)^6 & &:= (-7 + 59 + 69 + 1 + 406 + 2 - 5)^4 \\
 &:= (-75 + 4 - 1 + 8 + 8 + 90 + 6 + 25)^6 & &:= (-7 - 5 + 96 + 9 + 1 + 406 + 25)^4 \\
 &:= (7 + 54 + 18 + 8 + 9 - 06 - 25)^6 & &:= (-7 - 5 + 9 + 6 + 91 + 406 + 25)^4 \\
 &:= (-7 + 54 - 18 + 8 + 9 - 06 + 25)^6 & &:= (-75 + 96 + 91 + 406 + 2 + 5)^4 \\
 &:= (7 + 54 - 1 - 88 + 90 + 6 + 2 - 5)^6 & &:= (-7 + 596 - 91 - 40 + 62 + 5)^4 \\
 &:= (7 + 54 + 1 - 88 + 90 - 6 + 2 + 5)^6 & &:= (-7 + 596 + 9 - 140 + 62 + 5)^4 \\
 &:= (-7 + 54 + 1 - 8 - 8 + 90 - 62 + 5)^6 & &:= (-7 - 5 + 969 - 1 - 406 - 25)^4 \\
 &:= (-7 - 54 + 1 + 8 + 8 + 90 - 6 + 25)^6 & &**76024275625** := (76 + 024 + 275625)^2 \\
 &:= (7 + 5 + 41 + 88 - 9 - 062 - 5)^6 & &**76225024000** := (7 + 6 + 225 + 02 + 4000)^3 \\
 &:= (7 - 5 + 41 + 88 - 9 - 062 + 5)^6 & &**76440958784** := (76 + 4 + 4095 - 8 - 7 + 84)^3 \\
 &:= (7 + 5 + 4 + 18 + 8 + 90 - 62 - 5)^6 & &:= (7 - 6 + 4409 + 5 - 87 - 84)^3 \\
 &:= (7 - 5 + 4 + 18 + 8 + 90 - 62 + 5)^6 & &**76495006125** := (-764 + 9 + 5006 + 1 - 2 - 5)^3 \\
 &:= (7 + 5 + 4 - 18 + 8 + 90 - 6 - 25)^6 & &**76549608976** := (7 + 6 + 549 - 6 - 08 - 9 - 7 - 6)^4
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 &:= (7 - 6 + 549 + 6 - 08 - 9 - 7 - 6)^4 \\
 &:= (-7 + 6 + 549 - 6 - 08 - 9 + 7 - 6)^4 \\
 &:= (-7 - 6 + 549 + 6 - 08 - 9 + 7 - 6)^4 \\
 &:= (7 - 6 + 549 - 6 - 08 - 9 - 7 + 6)^4 \\
 &:= (-7 - 6 + 549 - 6 - 08 - 9 + 7 + 6)^4 \\
 &:= (7 + 6 + 5 + 496 + 08 - 9 + 7 + 6)^4 \\
 &:= (-76 - 5 + 4 - 9 + 608 - 9 + 7 + 6)^4 \\
 &:= (7 + 6 - 5 + 4 + 9 + 608 - 97 - 6)^4 \\
 &:= (-7 + 6 + 5 - 4 + 9 + 608 - 97 + 6)^4 \\
 &:= (7 - 6 - 5 + 4 + 9 + 608 - 97 + 6)^4 \\
 &:= (7 + 6 - 5 + 4 - 9 + 608 - 9 - 76)^4 \\
 &:= (76 + 549 - 6 - 08 - 9 - 76)^4 \\
 &:= (-76 + 549 - 6 - 08 - 9 + 76)^4 \\
 &:= (-76 - 5 + 496 + 08 + 97 + 6)^4 \\
 &:= (7 - 65 + 496 + 089 - 7 + 6)^4 \\
 &:= (-7 - 65 + 496 + 089 + 7 + 6)^4 \\
 &:= (-7 + 65 - 49 + 608 - 97 + 6)^4 \\
 \mathbf{76765625000} &:= (-7 - 676 - 5 - 62 + 5000)^3 \\
 \mathbf{77127842961} &:= (-771 + 278429 + 61)^2 \\
 \mathbf{77133397441} &:= (77 + 13 - 3 - 3 + 9 - 7 + 441)^4 \\
 &:= (77 - 13 + 3 + 3 + 9 + 7 + 441)^4 \\
 &:= (-77 - 133 + 3 - 9 + 744 - 1)^4 \\
 &:= (77 + 13 - 3 + 397 + 44 - 1)^4 \\
 &:= (77 + 13 + 3 + 397 - 4 + 41)^4 \\
 &:= (77 - 1 - 3 + 339 + 74 + 41)^4 \\
 \mathbf{77199941512} &:= (77 + 1 + 9 + 9 + 9 + 4151 + 2)^3 \\
 &:= (7 + 71 + 9 + 9 + 9 + 4151 + 2)^3 \\
 &:= (7 - 7 + 1 + 99 + 9 + 4151 - 2)^3 \\
 &:= (-7 + 7 + 1 + 99 + 9 + 4151 - 2)^3 \\
 &:= (7 + 7 + 1 + 99 - 9 + 4151 + 2)^3 \\
 &:= (7 - 7 + 1 + 9 + 99 + 4151 - 2)^3 \\
 &:= (-7 + 7 + 1 + 9 + 99 + 4151 - 2)^3 \\
 &:= (7 + 7 + 1 - 9 + 99 + 4151 + 2)^3 \\
 \mathbf{77417712728} &:= (-7 - 7 + 4177 + 127 - 28)^3 \\
 \mathbf{77635893096} &:= (776 + 3589 - 3 - 096)^3 \\
 \mathbf{77720518656} &:= (7 + 7 - 7 - 2 + 0518 + 6 + 5 - 6)^4 \\
 &:= (7 - 7 + 7 - 2 + 0518 + 6 + 5 - 6)^4 \\
 &:= (-7 + 7 + 7 - 2 + 0518 + 6 + 5 - 6)^4
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 &:= (7 + 7 - 7 - 2 + 0518 - 6 + 5 + 6)^4 \\
 &:= (7 - 7 + 7 - 2 + 0518 - 6 + 5 + 6)^4 \\
 &:= (-7 + 7 + 7 - 2 + 0518 - 6 + 5 + 6)^4 \\
 &:= (7 + 7 - 7 + 20 + 518 - 6 - 5 - 6)^4 \\
 &:= (7 - 7 + 7 + 20 + 518 - 6 - 5 - 6)^4 \\
 &:= (-7 + 7 + 7 + 20 + 518 - 6 - 5 - 6)^4 \\
 &:= (77 - 72 + 0518 + 6 + 5 - 6)^4 \\
 &:= (77 - 72 + 0518 - 6 + 5 + 6)^4 \\
 &:= (77 - 7 + 2 + 0518 - 6 - 56)^4 \\
 &:= (-7 + 77 + 2 + 0518 - 6 - 56)^4 \\
 &:= (7 - 7 + 720 + 5 - 186 - 5 - 6)^4 \\
 &:= (-7 + 7 + 720 + 5 - 186 - 5 - 6)^4 \\
 &:= (7 - 7 + 720 - 5 - 186 + 5 - 6)^4 \\
 &:= (-7 + 7 + 720 - 5 - 186 + 5 - 6)^4 \\
 &:= (7 - 7 + 72 + 0518 - 6 - 56)^4 \\
 &:= (-7 + 7 + 72 + 0518 - 6 - 56)^4 \\
 &:= (777 - 2 - 05 - 186 - 56)^4 \\
 &:= (77 + 7 - 205 + 1 - 8 + 656)^4 \\
 &:= (77 - 7 - 205 - 1 + 8 + 656)^4 \\
 &:= (-7 + 772 + 05 - 186 - 56)^4 \\
 &:= (7 + 77 - 205 + 1 - 8 + 656)^4 \\
 &:= (-7 + 77 - 205 - 1 + 8 + 656)^4 \\
 &:= (777 - 205 + 18 - 6 - 56)^4 \\
 \mathbf{78242718961} &:= (7824 + 271896 - 1)^2 \\
 \mathbf{78310985281} &:= (7 + 8 + 31 - 09 - 8 + 5 - 2 - 8 - 1)^8 \\
 &:= (7 - 8 + 31 - 09 + 8 + 5 - 2 - 8 - 1)^8 \\
 &:= (7 - 8 + 31 - 09 - 8 + 5 - 2 + 8 - 1)^8 \\
 &:= (-7 + 8 + 31 + 09 - 8 - 5 + 2 - 8 + 1)^8 \\
 &:= (-7 - 8 + 31 + 09 + 8 - 5 + 2 - 8 + 1)^8 \\
 &:= (-7 - 8 + 31 + 09 - 8 - 5 + 2 + 8 + 1)^8 \\
 &:= (7 + 8 - 3 + 10 + 9 + 8 - 5 - 2 - 8 - 1)^8 \\
 &:= (7 + 8 + 3 + 10 + 9 - 8 + 5 - 2 - 8 - 1)^8 \\
 &:= (7 - 8 + 3 + 10 + 9 + 8 + 5 - 2 - 8 - 1)^8 \\
 &:= (7 + 8 + 3 - 10 + 9 + 8 + 5 + 2 - 8 - 1)^8 \\
 &:= (-7 + 8 - 3 + 10 + 9 + 8 + 5 + 2 - 8 - 1)^8 \\
 &:= (7 + 8 - 3 + 10 + 9 - 8 - 5 - 2 + 8 - 1)^8 \\
 &:= (7 - 8 - 3 + 10 + 9 + 8 - 5 - 2 + 8 - 1)^8 \\
 &:= (7 - 8 + 3 + 10 + 9 - 8 + 5 - 2 + 8 - 1)^8
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} & := (-7+8+3+10-9+8+5-2+8-1)^8 & := (7+8-3-10-9+8-5+28-1)^8 \\ & := (7+8-3-10+9+8-5+2+8-1)^8 & := (7+8+3-10-9-8+5+28-1)^8 \\ & := (7+8+3-10+9-8+5+2+8-1)^8 & := (-7+8-3+10-9-8+5+28-1)^8 \\ & := (-7+8-3+10+9-8+5+2+8-1)^8 & := (7-8+3-10-9+8+5+28-1)^8 \\ & := (7-8+3-10+9+8+5+2+8-1)^8 & := (-7-8-3+10-9+8+5+28-1)^8 \\ & := (-7-8-3+10+9+8+5+2+8-1)^8 & := (7+8+3+10+9+8+5-28+1)^8 \\ & := (7+8+3+10-9+8+5-2-8+1)^8 & := (-7-8+3+10+9-8-5+28+1)^8 \\ & := (7+8-3+10+9-8+5+2-8+1)^8 & := (7-8-3+10-9-8+5+28+1)^8 \\ & := (7-8-3+10+9+8+5+2-8+1)^8 & := (-7+8-3-10+9-8+5+28+1)^8 \\ & := (7+8-3+10-9+8-5-2+8+1)^8 & := (-7-8-3-10+9+8+5+28+1)^8 \\ & := (7+8+3+10-9-8+5-2+8+1)^8 & := (7+8-3+1+098-5-2-81)^8 \\ & := (7-8+3+10-9+8+5-2+8+1)^8 & := (-7+8+3-1+098+5-2-81)^8 \\ & := (-7+8+3-10+9+8+5-2+8+1)^8 & := (7-8+3+1+098+5-2-81)^8 \\ & := (7-8-3+10+9-8+5+2+8+1)^8 & := (-7+8-3+1+098+5+2-81)^8 \\ & := (7+8+3-10-9+8+5+2+8+1)^8 & := (7+8+3+1-09-8+528-1)^4 \\ & := (-7+8-3+10-9+8+5+2+8+1)^8 & := (7-8+3-1+09-8+528-1)^4 \\ & := (-7+8-3-1-09-8+52-8-1)^8 & := (-7+8+3-1-09+8+528-1)^4 \\ & := (7-8-3+1-09-8+52-8-1)^8 & := (7-8+3+1-09+8+528-1)^4 \\ & := (-7-8-3-1-09+8+52-8-1)^8 & := (7+8+3-1-09-8+528+1)^4 \\ & := (-7-8-3-1-09-8+52+8-1)^8 & := (-7+8-3+1+09-8+528+1)^4 \\ & := (7-8-3-1-09-8+52-8+1)^8 & := (7-8+3-1-09+8+528+1)^4 \\ & := (-78+3-1+09+85-2+8-1)^8 & := (-7-8-3+1+09+8+528+1)^4 \\ & := (-78-3+1+09+85+2+8-1)^8 & := (7+8-3-1-09-8-52+81)^8 \\ & := (-78-3-1+09+85+2+8+1)^8 & := (7-8-3-1-09+8-52+81)^8 \\ & := (78-3-1-09-8-5-28-1)^8 & := (78+31-098+5-2+8+1)^8 \\ & := (78+3-1+09+8+5+2-81)^8 & := (-78+3-10+98+5-2+8-1)^8 \\ & := (-78-3-1+09+8+5+2+81)^8 & := (-78-3+10+98+5-2-8+1)^8 \\ & := (7-83+1+098-5-2+8-1)^8 & := (-78+3+10+98-5+2-8+1)^8 \\ & := (-7-83+1+098+5+2+8-1)^8 & := (-78-3-10+98+5+2+8+1)^8 \\ & := (7-83+1+098+5+2-8+1)^8 & := (78-3+10-9+8-52-8-1)^8 \\ & := (7-83-1+098-5-2+8+1)^8 & := (78-3+10-9-8-52+8-1)^8 \\ & := (-7-83-1+098+5+2+8+1)^8 & := (78-3-10+9+8-52-8+1)^8 \\ & := (-7-8-31-09+85+2-8-1)^8 & := (78-3-10+9-8-52+8+1)^8 \\ & := (7+8+31+09-8+5-28-1)^8 & := (78-3+1-098+52-8+1)^8 \\ & := (7-8+31+09+8+5-28-1)^8 & := (-78-3+1-09+85+28-1)^8 \\ & := (7+8-31+09+8-5+28-1)^8 & := (-78-3-1-09+85+28+1)^8 \\ & := (7+8+31-09+8+5-28+1)^8 & := (7-83+109-8+5+2-8-1)^8 \\ & := (-7-8+31-09-8-5+28+1)^8 & := (-7-83+109+8+5-2-8+1)^8 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} & := (-7 - 83 + 109 - 8 + 5 - 2 + 8 + 1)^8 & := (7 + 8 - 3 + 6 - 4 - 1 - 6 - 4 + 09 - 6)^{14} \\ & := (-7 - 83 + 10 + 9 + 85 + 2 + 8 - 1)^8 & := (-7 + 8 + 3 + 6 + 4 - 1 - 6 - 4 + 09 - 6)^{14} \\ & := (7 - 83 + 10 + 9 + 85 + 2 - 8 + 1)^8 & := (7 - 8 + 3 + 6 + 4 + 1 - 6 - 4 + 09 - 6)^{14} \\ & := (7 + 83 + 10 + 9 - 8 + 5 - 2 - 81)^8 & := (7 + 8 - 3 - 6 - 4 - 1 + 6 - 4 + 09 - 6)^{14} \\ & := (7 + 83 - 10 + 9 + 8 + 5 + 2 - 81)^8 & := (-7 + 8 + 3 - 6 + 4 - 1 + 6 - 4 + 09 - 6)^{14} \\ & := (7 - 83 + 10 + 9 - 8 + 5 + 2 + 81)^8 & := (-7 + 8 - 3 + 6 - 4 + 1 + 6 - 4 + 09 - 6)^{14} \\ & := (7 + 83 - 1 - 098 + 5 + 28 - 1)^8 & := (7 - 8 + 3 - 6 + 4 + 1 + 6 - 4 + 09 - 6)^{14} \\ & := (-7 + 8 - 31 + 098 - 52 + 8 - 1)^8 & := (-7 + 8 + 3 + 6 - 4 - 1 - 6 + 4 + 09 - 6)^{14} \\ & := (7 + 8 - 31 + 098 - 52 - 8 + 1)^8 & := (7 - 8 - 3 + 6 + 4 - 1 - 6 + 4 + 09 - 6)^{14} \\ & := (7 - 8 - 31 + 098 - 52 + 8 + 1)^8 & := (7 - 8 + 3 + 6 - 4 + 1 - 6 + 4 + 09 - 6)^{14} \\ & := (7 - 8 + 31 - 09 + 85 - 2 - 81)^8 & := (-7 + 8 + 3 - 6 - 4 - 1 + 6 + 4 + 09 - 6)^{14} \\ & := (-7 - 8 + 31 + 09 - 85 + 2 + 81)^8 & := (7 - 8 - 3 - 6 + 4 - 1 + 6 + 4 + 09 - 6)^{14} \\ & := (-7 + 8 + 3 + 109 - 85 + 2 - 8 + 1)^8 & := (7 - 8 + 3 - 6 - 4 + 1 + 6 + 4 + 09 - 6)^{14} \\ & := (-7 - 8 + 3 + 109 - 85 + 2 + 8 + 1)^8 & := (-7 - 8 - 3 + 6 + 4 + 1 + 6 + 4 + 09 - 6)^{14} \\ & := (7 - 8 - 3 + 109 - 8 + 5 + 2 - 81)^8 & := (7 + 8 - 3 + 6 + 4 + 1 + 6 + 4 + 09 - 6)^7 \\ & := (7 - 8 - 3 - 10 + 98 - 52 - 8 - 1)^8 & := (7 + 8 + 3 + 6 - 4 - 1 - 6 - 4 - 09 + 6)^{14} \\ & := (7 - 8 + 3 + 10 + 9 + 85 - 2 - 81)^8 & := (7 + 8 + 3 - 6 - 4 - 1 + 6 - 4 - 09 + 6)^{14} \\ & := (7 + 8 + 3 - 10 + 9 + 85 + 2 - 81)^8 & := (-7 + 8 - 3 + 6 + 4 - 1 + 6 - 4 - 09 + 6)^{14} \\ & := (-7 + 8 - 3 + 10 + 9 + 85 + 2 - 81)^8 & := (-7 + 8 + 3 + 6 - 4 + 1 + 6 - 4 - 09 + 6)^{14} \\ & := (-78 - 31 + 098 + 5 + 28 + 1)^8 & := (7 - 8 - 3 + 6 + 4 + 1 + 6 - 4 - 09 + 6)^{14} \\ & := (78 - 31 - 098 - 5 - 2 + 81)^8 & := (7 - 8 + 3 + 6 + 4 - 1 - 6 + 4 - 09 + 6)^{14} \\ & := (-78 - 31 - 09 + 8 + 52 + 81)^8 & := (7 + 8 - 3 - 6 + 4 + 1 - 6 + 4 - 09 + 6)^{14} \\ & := (78 + 3 - 109 + 8 + 52 - 8 - 1)^8 & := (-7 + 8 - 3 + 6 - 4 - 1 + 6 + 4 - 09 + 6)^{14} \\ & := (78 + 3 - 109 - 8 + 52 + 8 - 1)^8 & := (7 - 8 + 3 - 6 + 4 - 1 + 6 + 4 - 09 + 6)^{14} \\ & := (7 + 83 - 109 + 8 + 5 + 28 + 1)^8 & := (7 - 8 - 3 + 6 - 4 + 1 + 6 + 4 - 09 + 6)^{14} \\ & := (-7 - 83 + 10 - 9 + 85 + 28 - 1)^8 & := (-7 - 8 + 3 + 6 + 4 + 1 + 6 + 4 - 09 + 6)^{14} \\ & := (-7 - 83 - 10 + 9 + 85 + 28 + 1)^8 & := (7 + 8 + 3 + 6 + 4 + 1 + 6 + 4 - 09 + 6)^7 \\ & := (-7 - 8 - 310 + 9 + 852 - 8 + 1)^4 & := (7 + 8 - 3 - 6 - 4 - 1 - 6 - 4 + 09 + 6)^{14} \\ & := (-7 - 8 - 31 + 098 + 52 - 81)^8 & := (-7 + 8 + 3 - 6 + 4 - 1 - 6 - 4 + 09 + 6)^{14} \\ & := (7 + 8 + 3 - 109 + 85 + 28 + 1)^8 & := (-7 + 8 - 3 + 6 - 4 + 1 - 6 - 4 + 09 + 6)^{14} \\ & := (-7 + 8 - 3 - 10 - 98 + 52 + 81)^8 & := (7 - 8 + 3 - 6 + 4 + 1 - 6 - 4 + 09 + 6)^{14} \\ & := (78 + 310 + 98 + 52 - 8 - 1)^4 & := (-7 - 8 + 3 + 6 - 4 - 1 + 6 - 4 + 09 + 6)^{14} \\ & := (-7 + 83 - 109 + 85 - 28 - 1)^8 & := (7 + 8 + 3 + 6 - 4 - 1 + 6 - 4 + 09 + 6)^7 \\ & := (7 + 83 + 10 - 98 + 528 - 1)^4 & := (-7 + 8 - 3 - 6 - 4 + 1 + 6 - 4 + 09 + 6)^{14} \\ \mathbf{78364164096} & := (7 + 8 + 3 + 6 - 4 - 1 + 6 - 4 - 09 - 6)^{14} & := (-7 + 8 + 3 - 6 - 4 - 1 - 6 + 4 + 09 + 6)^{14} \\ & := (7 + 8 - 3 + 6 + 4 + 1 - 6 + 4 - 09 - 6)^{14} & := (7 - 8 - 3 - 6 + 4 - 1 - 6 + 4 + 09 + 6)^{14} \\ & := (7 - 8 + 3 + 6 + 4 - 1 + 6 + 4 - 09 - 6)^{14} & := (7 - 8 + 3 - 6 - 4 + 1 - 6 + 4 + 09 + 6)^{14} \\ & := (7 + 8 - 3 - 6 + 4 + 1 + 6 + 4 - 09 - 6)^{14} & := (-7 - 8 - 3 + 6 + 4 + 1 - 6 + 4 + 09 + 6)^{14} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} &:= (7+8-3+6+4+1-6+4+09+6)^7 & &:= (7-8-3+6+4-1-6+40-9+6)^7 \\ &:= (7-8+3+6+4-1+6+4+09+6)^7 & &:= (7-8+3+6-4+1-6+40-9+6)^7 \\ &:= (-7-8-3-6+4+1+6+4+09+6)^{14} & &:= (-7+8+3-6-4-1+6+40-9+6)^7 \\ &:= (7+8-3-6+4+1+6+4+09+6)^7 & &:= (7-8-3-6+4-1+6+40-9+6)^7 \\ &:= (-7+8-3+64-1-6-4-09-6)^7 & &:= (7-8+3-6-4+1+6+40-9+6)^7 \\ &:= (7-8-3+64+1-6-4-09-6)^7 & &:= (-7-8-3+6+4+1+6+40-9+6)^7 \\ &:= (-7-8+3+64+1-6+4-09-6)^7 & &:= (-7+8-3-6-4-1-6+40+9+6)^7 \\ &:= (7-8-3-6+41-6-4-09-6)^{14} & &:= (7-8-3-6-4+1-6+40+9+6)^7 \\ &:= (7-8+3+6+41+6-4-09-6)^7 & &:= (-7-8+3-6+4+1-6+40+9+6)^7 \\ &:= (-7-8+3-6+41-6+4-09-6)^{14} & &:= (78-36-4-1+6-4-09+6)^7 \\ &:= (7+8+3-6+41-6+4-09-6)^7 & &:= (78+3-6-4-16-4-09-6)^7 \\ &:= (7-8-3+6+41-6-4+09-6)^7 & &:= (78+3+6+4+1+6+4-096)^{14} \\ &:= (7-8-3-6+41+6-4+09-6)^7 & &:= (-78-3+6-4-1-6-4+096)^{14} \\ &:= (-7-8+3+6+41-6+4+09-6)^7 & &:= (-78-3-6-4-1+6-4+096)^{14} \\ &:= (-7-8+3-6+41+6+4+09-6)^7 & &:= (-78-3+6+4+1+6+4+096)^7 \\ &:= (7-8+3+6+41-6-4-09+6)^7 & &:= (-7+83-64-1+6+4-09-6)^{14} \\ &:= (7-8+3-6+41+6-4-09+6)^7 & &:= (-7+83-64+1-6-4+09-6)^{14} \\ &:= (-7-8-3+6+41+6+4-09+6)^7 & &:= (-7+83-64-1-6+4-09+6)^{14} \\ &:= (7-8-3-6+41-6-4+09+6)^7 & &:= (7-83+64+1+6-4+09+6)^{14} \\ &:= (-7-8+3-6+41-6+4+09+6)^7 & &:= (-7+83-64-1+6+4+09+6)^7 \\ &:= (-7+8-3-6-4-1+64-09-6)^7 & &:= (-7+83+6-41+6+4-09-6)^7 \\ &:= (7-8-3-6-4+1+64-09-6)^7 & &:= (7+83-6-41-6-4+09-6)^7 \\ &:= (-7-8+3-6+4+1+64-09-6)^7 & &:= (-7+83+6-41-6+4-09+6)^7 \\ &:= (-7+8-3-6-4-1-6+40-9-6)^{14} & &:= (-7+83-6-41+6+4-09+6)^7 \\ &:= (7-8-3-6-4+1-6+40-9-6)^{14} & &:= (-7+83+6+4-1-64-09-6)^{14} \\ &:= (-7-8+3-6+4+1-6+40-9-6)^{14} & &:= (-7+83-6-4+1-64+09-6)^{14} \\ &:= (7+8+3-6+4+1-6+40-9-6)^7 & &:= (-7+83-6+4-1-64-09+6)^{14} \\ &:= (-7+8+3+6-4-1+6+40-9-6)^7 & &:= (-7+83+6+4-1-64+09+6)^7 \\ &:= (7-8-3+6+4-1+6+40-9-6)^7 & &:= (7-83+6-4+1+64+09+6)^{14} \\ &:= (7-8+3+6-4+1+6+40-9-6)^7 & &:= (-7+83-6-4+1-6-40-9-6)^{14} \\ &:= (-7+8-3+6-4-1-6+40+9-6)^7 & &:= (-7+83+6+4-1+6-40-9-6)^7 \\ &:= (7-8+3-6+4-1-6+40+9-6)^7 & &:= (7+83-6-4-1-6-40+9-6)^7 \\ &:= (7-8-3+6-4+1-6+40+9-6)^7 & &:= (-7+83+6-4+1-6-40+9-6)^7 \\ &:= (-7-8+3+6+4+1-6+40+9-6)^7 & &:= (-7+83-6-4+1+6-40+9-6)^7 \\ &:= (-7+8-3-6-4-1+6+40+9-6)^7 & &:= (-7+83+6+4-1-6-40-9+6)^7 \\ &:= (7-8-3-6-4+1+6+40+9-6)^7 & &:= (-7+83-6+4-1+6-40-9+6)^7 \\ &:= (-7-8+3-6+4+1+6+40+9-6)^7 & &:= (-7+83-6-4+1-6-40+9+6)^7 \\ &:= (-7+8+3+6-4-1-6+40-9+6)^7 & &:= (-7+8+36+4-16-4-09-6)^{14} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} &:= (7-8+36+4+16-4-09-6)^7 &:= (78-3+6-4-16-40-9-6)^{14} \\ &:= (-7+8+36-4-16+4-09-6)^{14} &:= (78-3-6-4-16-40-9+6)^{14} \\ &:= (7-8+36-4+16+4-09-6)^7 &:= (78-3+6-4-16-40+9+6)^7 \\ &:= (7+8-36+4+16+4+09-6)^{14} &:= (-78+3+6+4+16+40+9+6)^{14} \\ &:= (-7+8+36+4-16-4+09+6)^7 &:= (78-3+6+4+1+6+40-96)^7 \\ &:= (-7+8+36-4-16+4+09+6)^7 &:= (7-83+64-1+64-09-6)^7 \\ &:= (-7+8+3+64-1-64+09-6)^{14} &:= (-7-83+64+1+64-09+6)^7 \\ &:= (7-8+3+64+1-64+09-6)^{14} &:= (7-83+64-1-6+40-9-6)^{14} \\ &:= (-7+8+3-64-1+64+09-6)^{14} &:= (-7-83+64+1+6+40-9-6)^{14} \\ &:= (7-8+3-64+1+64+09-6)^{14} &:= (7-83+64-1+6+40+9-6)^7 \\ &:= (-7+8+3+64-1-6-40-9-6)^{14} &:= (-7-83+64+1-6+40-9+6)^{14} \\ &:= (7-8+3+64+1-6-40-9-6)^{14} &:= (7+83-64-1+6-40+9+6)^{14} \\ &:= (-7+8+3+64-1+6-40+9-6)^7 &:= (7-83+64-1-6+40+9+6)^7 \\ &:= (7-8+3+64+1+6-40+9-6)^7 &:= (-7-83+64+1+6+40+9+6)^7 \\ &:= (-7+8+3+64-1-6-40+9+6)^7 &:= (-7-83+6+41+64-09-6)^{14} \\ &:= (7-8+3+64+1-6-40+9+6)^7 &:= (-7-83-6+41+64-09+6)^{14} \\ &:= (-7+8+3-6-41+64-09-6)^{14} &:= (7+83+6-41-64+09+6)^{14} \\ &:= (-7+8+3+6-41+64+09-6)^7 &:= (-7-83+6+41+64+09+6)^7 \\ &:= (-7+8+3-6-41+64+09+6)^7 &:= (7+83+6-41+6-40-9-6)^{14} \\ &:= (-7-8-3-6+41-6+40-9-6)^7 &:= (-7-83+6+41+6+40+9-6)^{14} \\ &:= (7-8+3+6+41-6-40+9-6)^{14} &:= (7+83+6-41-6-40-9+6)^{14} \\ &:= (7-8+3-6+41+6-40+9-6)^{14} &:= (7+83-6-41+6-40-9+6)^{14} \\ &:= (-7+8+3+6-41-6+40+9-6)^{14} &:= (7+83+6-41+6-40+9+6)^7 \\ &:= (-7+8+3-6-41+6+40+9-6)^{14} &:= (-7-83+6+41-6+40+9+6)^{14} \\ &:= (7-8-3+6+41+6-40-9+6)^{14} &:= (-7-83-6+41+6+40+9+6)^{14} \\ &:= (-7+8-3+6-41+6+40-9+6)^{14} &:= (7-83-6+4-16+4+096)^{14} \\ &:= (7-8+3-6+41-6-40+9+6)^{14} &:= (-7-83+6+4+16+4+096)^7 \\ &:= (-7+8+3-6-41-6+40+9+6)^{14} &:= (7+8+36+41+6+4-096)^{14} \\ &:= (78-36-41+6-4+09-6)^{14} &:= (-7-8-36-41+6-4+096)^{14} \\ &:= (-78+36+41+6+4-09+6)^{14} &:= (7+8-36-41+6-4+096)^7 \\ &:= (78-36-41-6-4+09+6)^{14} &:= (-7+8+36-4+16-40-9+6)^{14} \\ &:= (78-36-4-1+6-40+9-6)^{14} &:= (-7-8-36+4+16+40-9+6)^{14} \\ &:= (-78+36+4+1+6+40-9+6)^{14} &:= (7+8-36+4+16+40-9+6)^7 \\ &:= (78-36-4-1-6-40+9+6)^{14} &:= (7+8+36-4-16-40+9+6)^{14} \\ &:= (-78-3+64+16+4+09-6)^{14} &:= (7-8-36+4-16+40+9+6)^{14} \\ &:= (-78+3+64+16+4-09+6)^{14} &:= (7-8+36+4-1+64-096)^{14} \\ &:= (78-3-64-16-4+09+6)^{14} &:= (7+8-36-4-1-64+096)^{14} \\ &:= (78-3+6+41+6+4-096)^7 &:= (7+8+36+4+1+6+40-96)^{14} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} & := (-7-8-36-4-1+6-40+96)^{14} \\ & := (7+8-36-4-1+6-40+96)^7 \\ & := (7+8+3+64+16+4-096)^{14} \\ & := (-7+8-3-6+4-16-40+96)^7 \\ & := (78+36-41-64-09+6)^{14} \\ & := (-78-36+41+64+09+6)^{14} \\ & := (-78+36+41-6+40+9-6)^7 \\ & := (78+36-41+6-40-9+6)^7 \\ & := (-78-36+4+16+4+096)^{14} \\ & := (-78-3+64+16+40-9+6)^7 \\ & := (-7+83-6+4-164+096)^{14} \\ & := (-7+83+6-4-16+40-96)^{14} \\ & := (7-83+6+4+16-40+96)^{14} \\ & := (7-8-36+41-64+096)^7 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} & := (7-8+3+641-640+9-6)^{14} \\ & := (-7+8+3-641+640+9-6)^{14} \\ & := (7-8+3-64+164-096)^{14} \\ & := (-7-8-3+64+16+40-96)^{14} \\ & := (7+8-3+64+16+40-96)^7 \\ & := (-7+8-3-64+16-40+96)^{14} \\ & := (783-641-6-4-096)^7 \\ & := (783-6-4-1-640-96)^7 \\ & := (78-36+4+16+40-96)^{14} \\ & := (-7+8-364-16+409+6)^7 \\ & := (7-8+36+416-409-6)^7 \\ & := (-7+8+36-416+409+6)^7 \end{aligned}$$

78502725751 := (78+50+2+7-2+5+7+5-1)⁵

$$\begin{aligned} & := (78+50-2+7+2+5+7+5-1)^5 \\ & := (78+5+02+72+5-7-5+1)^5 \\ & := (78+5-02+72-5+7-5+1)^5 \\ & := (78-5-02+72+5+7-5+1)^5 \\ & := (78+5+02+72-5-7+5+1)^5 \\ & := (78-5+02+72+5-7+5+1)^5 \\ & := (78-5-02+72-5+7+5+1)^5 \\ & := (78+5+02+7-2+57+5-1)^5 \\ & := (78+5-02+7+2+57+5-1)^5 \\ & := (78+5-02-7-2+5+75-1)^5 \\ & := (78-5+02+7-2-5+75+1)^5 \\ & := (78+5+02-7+2-5+75+1)^5 \\ & := (78-5-02+7+2-5+75+1)^5 \\ & := (78-5+02-7+2+5+75+1)^5 \\ & := (7+8+50-2+72+5+7+5-1)^5 \\ & := (7+8+50+2+7-2+5+75-1)^5 \\ & := (7+8+50-2+7+2+5+75-1)^5 \\ & := (7+8+5-02+72+57+5-1)^5 \\ & := (7+8-5-02+72-5+75+1)^5 \\ & := (-7+8+5+02+72-5+75+1)^5 \\ & := (-7+8-5+02+72+5+75+1)^5 \\ & := (78+50+27+2+5-7-5+1)^5 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} & := (78+50+27-2-5+7-5+1)^5 \\ & := (78+50+27+2-5-7+5+1)^5 \\ & := (78+50+2+7+25-7-5+1)^5 \\ & := (78+50+2-7+25+7-5+1)^5 \\ & := (78-5+027-2+57-5+1)^5 \\ & := (78+5+027+2-5-7+51)^5 \\ & := (78-5+027+2+5-7+51)^5 \\ & := (78-5+027-2-5+7+51)^5 \\ & := (78-5+02+7+25-7+51)^5 \\ & := (78-5+02-7+25+7+51)^5 \\ & := (7+8+50+27-2+57+5-1)^5 \\ & := (-7+8+50+27+2-5+75+1)^5 \\ & := (78-50-2+72+57-5+1)^5 \\ & := (78+50+2+72-57+5+1)^5 \\ & := (78-50+2+72+5-7+51)^5 \\ & := (78-50-2+72-5+7+51)^5 \\ & := (-78+5-027+257-5-1)^5 \\ & := (-78-5-027+257+5-1)^5 \\ & := (78-5+027-25+75+1)^5 \\ & := (78+5+02+72-57+51)^5 \\ & := (78+50+27+2-57+51)^5 \\ & := (-78+50-27+257-51)^5 \end{aligned}$$

78843215872 := (-78-8+4321+58-7+2)³

$$\begin{aligned}
 \mathbf{79119341757} &:= (7 + 91 + 1 + 9 + 3 + 4175 + 7)^3 &:= (81 + 1 + 36 + 8 + 1 + 20 + 3 + 2)^5 \\
 &:= (7 + 9 + 1 + 1 + 93 + 4175 + 7)^3 &:= (81 - 1 - 3 + 68 + 12 - 03 - 2)^5 \\
 \mathbf{79174644184} &:= (79 + 17 + 4 + 6 + 4 + 4184)^3 &:= (81 + 1 + 3 + 6 + 8 + 1 + 20 + 32)^5 \\
 \mathbf{79451542899} &:= (7 + 9 + 4 + 5 - 1 - 5 + 4289 - 9)^3 &:= (8 + 113 + 6 + 8 + 12 + 03 + 2)^5 \\
 &:= (7 + 9 + 4 - 5 - 1 + 5 + 4289 - 9)^3 &:= (8 + 113 - 6 + 8 - 1 - 2 + 032)^5 \\
 &:= (7 + 9 - 4 - 5 - 1 - 5 + 4289 + 9)^3 &:= (8 + 113 + 6 - 8 - 1 + 2 + 032)^5 \\
 &:= (7 - 9 + 4 + 5 - 1 - 5 + 4289 + 9)^3 &:= (-8 + 113 + 6 + 8 - 1 + 2 + 032)^5 \\
 &:= (7 - 9 + 4 - 5 - 1 + 5 + 4289 + 9)^3 &:= (8 - 1 + 136 - 8 + 12 + 03 + 2)^5 \\
 &:= (79 - 4 - 51 - 5 + 4289 - 9)^3 &:= (-8 - 1 + 136 + 8 + 12 + 03 + 2)^5 \\
 &:= (79 - 45 - 15 + 4289 - 9)^3 &:= (-8 + 1 + 136 - 8 + 1 - 2 + 032)^5 \\
 \mathbf{79502005521} &:= (7 + 9 + 502 + 005 + 5 + 2 + 1)^4 &:= (-8 - 1 + 136 - 8 - 1 + 2 + 032)^5 \\
 &:= (-7 + 9 + 5 - 02 + 005 + 521)^4 &:= (8 + 1 + 1 + 36 + 81 + 20 + 3 + 2)^5 \\
 &:= (7 - 9 + 5 + 02 + 005 + 521)^4 &:= (-8 + 1 + 1 - 36 - 8 + 1 + 203 - 2)^5 \\
 &:= (7 - 9 + 502 + 005 + 5 + 21)^4 &:= (-8 + 1 - 1 - 36 - 8 - 1 + 203 + 2)^5 \\
 \mathbf{79673526127} &:= (7 - 967 - 3 + 5261 - 2 + 7)^3 &:= (-8 - 1 + 1 - 36 - 8 - 1 + 203 + 2)^5 \\
 &:= (796 + 7 + 3526 + 1 - 27)^3 &:= (-8 - 1 - 1 - 36 - 8 + 1 + 203 + 2)^5 \\
 \mathbf{80102584576} &:= (-8 + 01 - 025 - 8 - 4 + 576)^4 &:= (8 + 1 + 1 + 3 + 6 + 81 + 20 + 32)^5 \\
 &:= (8 + 01 + 02 + 584 - 57 - 6)^4 &:= (81 - 13 + 68 + 1 + 20 - 3 - 2)^5 \\
 &:= (8 + 01 + 02 + 58 + 457 + 6)^4 &:= (81 + 13 + 6 + 8 + 12 + 032)^5 \\
 &:= (80 - 10 - 2 + 5 + 8 + 457 - 6)^4 &:= (-81 + 13 + 6 + 8 + 1 + 203 + 2)^5 \\
 &:= (80 - 10 + 2 + 5 - 8 + 457 + 6)^4 &:= (81 + 1 - 36 + 81 + 20 + 3 + 2)^5 \\
 &:= (-80 - 1 + 025 + 8 + 4 + 576)^4 &:= (81 - 1 + 36 - 8 + 12 + 032)^5 \\
 &:= (-8 + 0102 - 5 - 8 + 457 - 6)^4 &:= (-81 + 1 + 36 - 8 - 1 + 203 + 2)^5 \\
 \mathbf{80453723013} &:= (8 + 04537 - 230 - 1 + 3)^3 &:= (-81 - 1 + 36 - 8 + 1 + 203 + 2)^5 \\
 &:= (80 + 4537 - 2 - 301 + 3)^3 &:= (81 - 1 - 3 + 6 + 81 + 20 - 32)^5 \\
 \mathbf{80612837776} &:= (80 + 61 + 283777 + 6)^2 &:= (-8 + 11 + 36 - 8 + 120 + 3 - 2)^5 \\
 \mathbf{80706559921} &:= (8 - 070 - 6 + 5 + 599 - 2 - 1)^4 &:= (8 + 11 - 3 - 68 - 1 + 203 + 2)^5 \\
 &:= (-8 - 070 + 6 + 5 + 599 + 2 - 1)^4 &:= (8 + 11 + 3 + 6 - 81 + 203 + 2)^5 \\
 &:= (-80 + 70 - 6 + 559 - 9 - 2 + 1)^4 &:= (8 - 1 + 13 - 68 - 1 + 203 - 2)^5 \\
 &:= (80 - 7 - 06 + 559 - 92 - 1)^4 &:= (8 + 1 + 13 + 6 - 81 + 203 + 2)^5 \\
 &:= (8 - 070 + 6 + 559 + 9 + 21)^4 &:= (-8 - 1 - 1 + 368 - 1 - 203 - 2)^5 \\
 &:= (80 - 70 - 6 + 559 - 9 - 21)^4 &:= (-8 + 1 - 1 + 36 - 81 + 203 + 2)^5 \\
 \mathbf{80733594248} &:= (8 + 073 - 3 + 5 - 9 + 4248)^3 &:= (-8 - 1 + 1 + 36 - 81 + 203 + 2)^5 \\
 &:= (8 + 07 + 3 - 3 + 59 + 4248)^3 &:= (811 + 3 - 681 + 20 - 3 + 2)^5 \\
 &:= (8 + 07 - 3 + 3 + 59 + 4248)^3 &:= (811 - 3 - 681 + 20 + 3 + 2)^5 \\
 \mathbf{81136812032} &:= (8 + 1 + 1 + 3 + 6 + 8 + 120 + 3 + 2)^5 &:= (-8 + 113 - 68 + 120 - 3 - 2)^5 \\
 &:= (81 - 13 + 6 + 81 + 2 - 03 - 2)^5 &:= (8 + 1 - 13 + 68 + 120 - 32)^5 \\
 &:= (81 - 13 + 6 + 81 - 2 - 03 + 2)^5 &:= (81 - 13 - 68 + 120 + 32)^5
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} & := (-81 + 13 + 68 + 120 + 32)^5 \\ \mathbf{81313944336} & := (81 + 3 + 1 - 3 + 9 + 4 + 433 + 6)^4 \\ & := (81 - 3 + 1 + 3 + 9 + 4 + 433 + 6)^4 \\ & := (81 + 31 - 3 - 9 + 443 - 3 - 6)^4 \\ & := (81 - 3 + 13 + 9 + 443 - 3 - 6)^4 \\ & := (81 + 3 + 13 - 9 + 443 - 3 + 6)^4 \\ & := (81 - 3 + 13 - 9 + 443 + 3 + 6)^4 \\ & := (-8 + 131 - 3 - 9 - 4 + 433 - 6)^4 \\ & := (-8 + 13 - 1 - 3 + 94 + 433 + 6)^4 \\ & := (-8 - 1 - 3 + 13 + 94 + 433 + 6)^4 \\ & := (813 + 1 + 3 + 9 + 44 - 336)^4 \\ & := (81 + 313 + 94 + 43 - 3 + 6)^4 \\ & := (-81 + 3 + 1 + 3 + 944 - 336)^4 \\ & := (8 + 131 - 39 + 443 - 3 - 6)^4 \\ & := (8 + 131 - 3 - 9 + 443 - 36)^4 \\ & := (-8 - 1 - 3 + 139 + 443 - 36)^4 \\ & := (-81 - 3 + 139 + 443 + 36)^4 \\ \mathbf{81464295375} & := (8 + 1 + 46 + 4295 - 3 - 7 - 5)^3 \\ & := (-8 + 1 + 46 + 4295 + 3 - 7 + 5)^3 \\ & := (81 - 46 + 4295 + 3 + 7 - 5)^3 \\ \mathbf{81520685056} & := (-8 - 1 + 5206 - 850 - 5 - 6)^3 \\ \mathbf{81633542472} & := (-8 - 1 + 63 + 35 + 4247 + 2)^3 \\ \mathbf{81828607249} & := (8 - 18 + 286072 + 4 - 9)^2 \\ \mathbf{81916141607} & := (-8 + 191 + 6 + 1 + 4160 - 7)^3 \\ & := (-8 + 191 - 6 - 1 + 4160 + 7)^3 \\ \mathbf{81924750625} & := (-81 + 9 - 2 - 4 - 7 - 5 + 0625)^4 \\ & := (-81 - 9 + 2 - 4 + 7 - 5 + 0625)^4 \\ & := (-81 - 9 - 2 + 4 - 7 + 5 + 0625)^4 \\ & := (8 + 19 - 2 + 4 + 7 + 506 - 2 - 5)^4 \\ & := (8 + 19 + 2 - 4 + 7 + 506 + 2 - 5)^4 \\ & := (8 + 19 + 2 + 4 - 7 + 506 - 2 + 5)^4 \\ & := (8 + 19 - 2 + 4 - 7 + 506 + 2 + 5)^4 \\ & := (-81 + 92 + 4 + 7 + 506 + 2 + 5)^4 \\ & := (8 + 19 + 2 + 475 + 06 + 25)^4 \\ & := (-8 - 19 + 2 + 47 + 506 + 2 + 5)^4 \\ & := (-8 - 19 - 2 - 4 - 7 - 50 + 625)^4 \\ & := (-8 - 1 + 92 - 47 + 506 - 2 - 5)^4 \\ & := (819 - 247 - 50 + 6 + 2 + 5)^4 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} & := (81 - 92 + 47 + 506 - 2 - 5)^4 \\ & := (81 - 92 - 4 - 75 + 0625)^4 \\ & := (-8 - 192 + 4 + 750 + 6 - 25)^4 \\ & := (-8 - 19 + 24 + 7 + 506 + 25)^4 \\ & := (8 + 1 + 92 - 47 + 506 - 25)^4 \\ & := (819 + 247 - 506 - 25)^4 \\ \mathbf{82142689923} & := (-8 + 2 - 1 + 4268 - 9 + 92 + 3)^3 \\ \mathbf{82286938449} & := (-82 + 286938 - 4 - 4 + 9)^2 \\ \mathbf{82426462208} & := (82 + 4264 - 6 + 2 + 2 + 08)^3 \\ \mathbf{82538991616} & := (-8 + 2 + 538 + 9 + 9 - 1 - 6 - 1 - 6)^4 \\ & := (8 + 2 + 538 + 9 - 9 + 1 - 6 - 1 - 6)^4 \\ & := (8 + 2 + 538 - 9 + 9 + 1 - 6 - 1 - 6)^4 \\ & := (8 + 2 + 538 + 9 - 9 - 1 - 6 + 1 - 6)^4 \\ & := (8 + 2 + 538 - 9 + 9 - 1 - 6 + 1 - 6)^4 \\ & := (-8 - 2 + 538 + 9 + 9 + 1 - 6 + 1 - 6)^4 \\ & := (8 - 2 + 538 - 9 - 9 - 1 + 6 - 1 + 6)^4 \\ & := (8 + 2 + 5 - 3 + 8 - 99 - 1 + 616)^4 \\ & := (8 + 2 + 5 - 3 + 8 - 9 - 91 + 616)^4 \\ & := (82 + 538 - 9 - 9 + 1 - 61 - 6)^4 \\ & := (8 - 2 - 5 + 389 + 91 + 61 - 6)^4 \\ & := (-8 + 2 - 5 + 389 + 91 + 61 + 6)^4 \\ & := (8 - 2 - 5 + 389 - 9 + 161 - 6)^4 \\ & := (-8 + 2 - 5 + 389 - 9 + 161 + 6)^4 \\ & := (82 - 538 + 991 + 6 + 1 - 6)^4 \\ & := (82 - 538 + 991 - 6 + 1 + 6)^4 \\ & := (8 - 25 + 389 + 9 + 161 - 6)^4 \\ \mathbf{82653950016} & := (8 + 2 + 6 + 53 + 9 - 5 - 001 - 6)^6 \\ & := (8 + 2 - 6 + 53 + 9 + 5 + 001 - 6)^6 \\ & := (8 + 2 - 6 + 53 + 9 - 5 - 001 + 6)^6 \\ & := (8 - 2 + 6 + 53 - 9 + 5 - 001 + 6)^6 \\ & := (8 - 2 + 6 + 5 + 39 + 5 - 001 + 6)^6 \\ & := (-8 - 2 - 6 - 5 - 3 + 95 + 001 - 6)^6 \\ & := (8 - 2 + 6 + 5 - 3 + 9 + 50 - 01 - 6)^6 \\ & := (8 + 2 + 6 - 5 + 3 + 9 + 50 - 01 - 6)^6 \\ & := (8 + 2 - 6 + 5 + 3 + 9 + 50 + 01 - 6)^6 \\ & := (8 - 2 + 6 + 5 + 3 - 9 + 50 - 01 + 6)^6 \\ & := (8 - 2 - 6 + 5 - 3 + 9 + 50 - 01 + 6)^6 \\ & := (-8 + 2 + 6 + 5 - 3 + 9 + 50 - 01 + 6)^6 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 &:= (8+2-6-5+3+9+50-01+6)^6 & &:= (-8-315+66+801-6-1)^4 \\
 &:= (8+2+6+5-3-9+50+01+6)^6 & \mathbf{83224499896} &:= (-8-32+2+4499-89-6)^3 \\
 &:= (82+6+5-39+5+001+6)^6 & \mathbf{83338924032} &:= (8-3+338-9+2+4032)^3 \\
 &:= (82+6+5+3-9-5-0016)^6 & \mathbf{83352886681} &:= (8-3+35+288668+1)^2 \\
 &:= (82-6+5-3+9-5-0016)^6 & \mathbf{83396175409} &:= (8+3+3961-7-5+409)^3 \\
 &:= (82+6-5+3-9+5-0016)^6 & &:= (-83-3-961+7+5409)^3 \\
 &:= (82-6-5-3+9+5-0016)^6 & \mathbf{83625443117} &:= (8+36+2+5+4+4311+7)^3 \\
 &:= (8+26+53-9-5-001-6)^6 & &:= (8-3-62+5+4431+1-7)^3 \\
 &:= (8+26+5+39-5-001-6)^6 & &:= (8+3+6-2+54+4311-7)^3 \\
 &:= (8+26-5+39+5-001-6)^6 & &:= (8-3-6+2+54+4311+7)^3 \\
 &:= (-8-26-5+3+95+001+6)^6 & &:= (-83+6+25+4431+1-7)^3 \\
 &:= (8+26-5+3-9+50-01-6)^6 & &:= (-83-6+25+4431-1+7)^3 \\
 &:= (-8+26+5-3-9+50-01+6)^6 & &:= (-8-36-2+5+4431-17)^3 \\
 &:= (8+26+5-3+9+5+0016)^6 & \mathbf{83740234375} &:= (8+37-40-2-3+4375)^3 \\
 &:= (8+2+65+3+9-5-0016)^6 & &:= (-8-37+40+2+3+4375)^3 \\
 &:= (8-2+65-3+9+5-0016)^6 & &:= (-83-7+4023+437+5)^3 \\
 &:= (82-65+39+5-001+6)^6 & \mathbf{83777829136} &:= (-8+377-7+82+91-3+6)^4 \\
 &:= (82-65-3+9+50-01-6)^6 & &:= (83+77+78+291+3+6)^4 \\
 &:= (82-65+3-9+50-01+6)^6 & &:= (8377-7829-1-3-6)^4 \\
 &:= (-8+2-6+53-9+50-016)^6 & \mathbf{83841135993} &:= (83+8+4+1+1+35+9+9+3)^5 \\
 &:= (-8+2-6+5+39+50-016)^6 & &:= (83+8-4-1-1+3+59+9-3)^5 \\
 &:= (82+6+53-9-50-016)^6 & &:= (83+8+4+1+1+3+59-9+3)^5 \\
 &:= (82-6-53+9+50-016)^6 & &:= (83+8-4-1-1-3+59+9+3)^5 \\
 &:= (82+6+5+39-50-016)^6 & &:= (83-8+4+1-1+3+59+9+3)^5 \\
 &:= (82-6-5-39+50-016)^6 & &:= (83-8+4-1+1+3+59+9+3)^5 \\
 &:= (8+26+5-39+50+016)^6 & &:= (83-8+4-1-1-3-5-9+93)^5 \\
 &:= (-8-26-5+39+50+016)^6 & &:= (83-8-4+1-1+3-5-9+93)^5 \\
 &:= (8-2+65-39+50-016)^6 & &:= (83-8-4-1+1+3-5-9+93)^5 \\
 &:= (-826-53+950+01-6)^6 & &:= (8+3+84+1+1+35+9+9+3)^5 \\
 &:= (8+26+539-500-1-6)^6 & &:= (8-3+84+1+1-3+59+9-3)^5 \\
 \mathbf{83156680161} &:= (-8+3+1+566-8-016-1)^4 & &:= (8+3+84+1+1+3+59-9+3)^5 \\
 &:= (-8+3-1+566-8-016+1)^4 & &:= (-8+3+84+1-1+3+59+9+3)^5 \\
 &:= (-83+1-5+6+680-1-61)^4 & &:= (-8+3+84-1+1+3+59+9+3)^5 \\
 &:= (-83+1+5-6+680+1-61)^4 & &:= (-8+3+84-1-1-3-5-9+93)^5 \\
 &:= (-83-1-5+6+680+1-61)^4 & &:= (-8-3+84-1-1+3-5-9+93)^5 \\
 &:= (8+31+566-8+01-61)^4 & &:= (8+3+8+41-1+3-5+99-3)^5 \\
 &:= (-8+31+566+8+01-61)^4 & &:= (8-3+8+41+1-3+5+99-3)^5 \\
 &:= (8-3-156+680+1+6+1)^4 & &:= (8+3+8+41-1-3-5+99+3)^5
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 &:= (8-3+8+41-1+3-5+99+3)^5 & &:= (8+3+8+4+11+35-9+93)^5 \\
 &:= (8+3-8+41-1+3+5+99+3)^5 & &:= (8+3+8-4-11-3+59+93)^5 \\
 &:= (-8+3+8+41-1+3+5+99+3)^5 & &:= (8-3-8-4+11-3+59+93)^5 \\
 &:= (8+3+8+41+1+3+5-9+93)^5 & &:= (-8-3+8-4+11-3+59+93)^5 \\
 &:= (8+3+8+41-1-3-5+9+93)^5 & &:= (8-3+8-4-11+3+59+93)^5 \\
 &:= (8-3+8+41-1+3-5+9+93)^5 & &:= (8+3+8-4-1-13+59+93)^5 \\
 &:= (8+3-8+41-1+3+5+9+93)^5 & &:= (-838+4+1+1-3-5+993)^5 \\
 &:= (-8+3+8+41-1+3+5+9+93)^5 & &:= (-838-4+1-1-3+5+993)^5 \\
 &:= (83+84-1+13-5-9-9-3)^5 & &:= (-838-4-1+1-3+5+993)^5 \\
 &:= (83+84+1-13-5+9-9+3)^5 & &:= (83+8-4+113-59+9+3)^5 \\
 &:= (83+84+1-13-5-9+9+3)^5 & &:= (-83+8-4+1+135+99-3)^5 \\
 &:= (83+84+1-1-35+9+9+3)^5 & &:= (8+38+41+13+59-9+3)^5 \\
 &:= (83+84-1+1-35+9+9+3)^5 & &:= (8+38+41-13-5-9+93)^5 \\
 &:= (83+8+41+13+5+9-9+3)^5 & &:= (8+38+41-1-35+99+3)^5 \\
 &:= (83+8+41+13+5-9+9+3)^5 & &:= (8+38+41-1-35+9+93)^5 \\
 &:= (83+8+41+1+35-9-9+3)^5 & &:= (8+38-41-1-3+59+93)^5 \\
 &:= (83-8+41-1+35+9-9+3)^5 & &:= (8-3-84+1+135+99-3)^5 \\
 &:= (83-8+41-1+35-9+9+3)^5 & &:= (83+8+41-13-59+93)^5 \\
 &:= (83+8-41-1+3+5+99-3)^5 & & \mathbf{83942893441} := (-8+394+289344-1)^2 \\
 &:= (83+8-41-1-3+5+99+3)^5 & & \mathbf{84102900025} := (-8-4+10+290002+5)^2 \\
 &:= (83+8-41-1-3+5+9+93)^5 & & \mathbf{84142830968} := (8+4-1+4283+096-8)^3 \\
 &:= (8+38+4+113+5-9-9+3)^5 & & \quad := (-8+4-1+4283+096+8)^3 \\
 &:= (8+38-4+113-5+9-9+3)^5 & & \mathbf{84200449887} := (84-200+4498+8-7)^3 \\
 &:= (8+38-4+113-5-9+9+3)^5 & & \mathbf{84258095104} := (8+4258+09+5+104)^3 \\
 &:= (8+38-4+11+3-5+99+3)^5 & & \mathbf{84290347584} := (-8-4+290347+5-8-4)^2 \\
 &:= (8+38+4+11+3+5-9+93)^5 & & \mathbf{84315766625} := (8+4315-7+66+6+2-5)^3 \\
 &:= (8+38-4+11+3-5+9+93)^5 & & \quad := (8+4315-7+6+66+2-5)^3 \\
 &:= (-8+38+4-1+135-9-9+3)^5 & & \quad := (8+4315-7+6+6+62-5)^3 \\
 &:= (8+38+4-1+13-5+99-3)^5 & & \quad := (8+4315+7-6-6+62+5)^3 \\
 &:= (8+38-4+1+13-5+99+3)^5 & & \quad := (-8+4315-7+66-6+25)^3 \\
 &:= (-8+38+4-1+13+5+99+3)^5 & & \quad := (-8+4315-7-6+66+25)^3 \\
 &:= (8+38+4+1+13+5-9+93)^5 & & \mathbf{84373464456} := (8+4373+4-6+4+4+5-6)^3 \\
 &:= (8+38-4+1+13-5+9+93)^5 & & \quad := (8+4373-4+6-4-4+5+6)^3 \\
 &:= (-8+38+4-1+13+5+9+93)^5 & & \quad := (-8+4373+4+6+4-4+5+6)^3 \\
 &:= (-8+38+4+1-1+35-9+93)^5 & & \quad := (-8+4373+4+6-4+4+5+6)^3 \\
 &:= (-8+38+4-1+1+35-9+93)^5 & & \quad := (-8+4373-4+6+4+4+5+6)^3 \\
 &:= (8-3-8-4+113+59-9-3)^5 & & \quad := (8-4-3-73-4+6+4456)^3 \\
 &:= (-8-3+8-4+113+59-9-3)^5 & & \quad := (-8+4-3-73+4+6+4456)^3
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 & := (-8 + 4373 - 4 + 64 - 45 + 6)^3 \\
 & := (8 - 43 - 7 - 34 + 6 + 4456)^3 \\
 \mathbf{84402451441} & := (8 + 4 + 4 + 02 + 4 + 514 + 4 - 1)^4 \\
 & := (84 + 4 + 02 + 4 + 5 - 1 + 441)^4 \\
 & := (-8 + 44 - 02 - 4 + 514 - 4 - 1)^4 \\
 & := (-8 + 4 + 40 - 2 - 4 + 514 - 4 - 1)^4 \\
 & := (-8 - 4 + 40 - 2 + 4 + 514 - 4 - 1)^4 \\
 & := (-8 - 4 + 40 - 2 - 4 + 514 + 4 - 1)^4 \\
 & := (84 + 402 + 45 + 1 + 4 + 4 - 1)^4 \\
 & := (84 + 402 + 45 - 1 + 4 + 4 + 1)^4 \\
 & := (84 + 402 + 4 + 5 + 1 + 44 - 1)^4 \\
 & := (84 + 402 + 4 + 5 - 1 + 44 + 1)^4 \\
 & := (84 + 402 + 4 + 5 - 1 + 4 + 41)^4 \\
 & := (84 - 4 + 024 - 5 - 1 + 441)^4 \\
 & := (8 + 440 + 2 + 45 + 1 + 44 - 1)^4 \\
 & := (8 + 440 + 2 + 45 - 1 + 44 + 1)^4 \\
 & := (8 + 440 + 2 + 45 - 1 + 4 + 41)^4 \\
 & := (8 + 44 - 024 + 514 - 4 + 1)^4 \\
 & := (8 + 44 + 02 + 45 - 1 + 441)^4 \\
 & := (8 + 4 + 40 - 24 + 514 - 4 + 1)^4 \\
 & := (8 - 4 + 40 - 24 + 514 + 4 + 1)^4 \\
 & := (8 + 4 + 40 + 2 + 45 - 1 + 441)^4 \\
 & := (8 + 4 - 4 - 024 + 514 + 41)^4 \\
 & := (8 - 4 + 4 - 024 + 514 + 41)^4 \\
 & := (84 - 40 - 24 + 514 + 4 + 1)^4 \\
 \mathbf{84488939072} & := (8 - 4 + 488 - 9 + 3907 - 2)^3 \\
 \mathbf{84662348471} & := (8 - 466 - 2 + 3 + 4847 + 1)^3 \\
 \mathbf{84720204288} & := (8 + 4 + 72 + 020 + 4288)^3 \\
 \mathbf{84835994984} & := (8 - 4 + 8 - 3 - 599 + 4984)^3 \\
 & := (848 + 3599 - 49 - 8 + 4)^3 \\
 \mathbf{84893929875} & := (-8 - 4893 + 9298 - 7 + 5)^3 \\
 \mathbf{85030560000} & := (-8 - 50 + 3 - 05 + 600 + 00)^4 \\
 & := (-85 + 030 - 5 + 600 + 00)^4 \\
 \mathbf{85125933199} & := (8 + 5125 - 933 + 199)^3 \\
 \mathbf{85292034304} & := (8 + 5 + 292034 - 3 + 04)^2 \\
 \mathbf{85649485312} & := (-8 - 5 + 6 + 4948 - 531 - 2)^3 \\
 & := (-8 + 56 - 4 - 948 + 5312)^3 \\
 \mathbf{85662167761} & := (-85 + 6 + 621 + 6 + 7 - 7 - 6 - 1)^4
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 & := (-85 + 6 + 621 + 6 - 7 + 7 - 6 - 1)^4 \\
 & := (-85 + 6 + 621 - 6 + 7 - 7 + 6 - 1)^4 \\
 & := (-85 - 6 + 621 + 6 + 7 - 7 + 6 - 1)^4 \\
 & := (-85 + 6 + 621 - 6 - 7 + 7 + 6 - 1)^4 \\
 & := (-85 - 6 + 621 + 6 - 7 + 7 + 6 - 1)^4 \\
 & := (-85 + 6 + 621 + 6 - 7 - 7 + 6 + 1)^4 \\
 & := (8 + 566 + 2 - 16 - 7 - 7 - 6 + 1)^4 \\
 & := (8 + 566 - 2 + 16 + 7 + 7 - 61)^4 \\
 & := (8 + 5 + 662 + 1 - 67 - 7 - 61)^4 \\
 & := (8 - 5 + 6 - 6 - 216 - 7 + 761)^4 \\
 & := (8 - 5 - 6 + 6 - 216 - 7 + 761)^4 \\
 & := (-85 + 6 + 621 + 67 - 7 - 61)^4 \\
 & := (8 + 56 + 621 - 67 - 76 - 1)^4 \\
 & := (8 + 56 + 621 - 6 - 77 - 61)^4 \\
 & := (8 - 56 - 6 - 21 + 677 - 61)^4 \\
 & := (8 - 5 + 6 - 62 - 167 + 761)^4 \\
 \mathbf{85824478531} & := (-8 - 58 - 2 + 4478 + 5 - 3 - 1)^3 \\
 & := (-8 - 58 + 2 + 4478 - 5 + 3 - 1)^3 \\
 & := (-8 + 5 - 8 - 2 + 4478 - 53 - 1)^3 \\
 \mathbf{85941272997} & := (8 - 5 - 9 + 4127 + 299 - 7)^3 \\
 \mathbf{86233722632} & := (8 + 623 + 3722 + 63 + 2)^3 \\
 \mathbf{86297287696} & := (8 + 629 - 7 + 2 - 87 - 6 + 9 - 6)^4 \\
 & := (-8 + 629 + 7 - 2 - 87 + 6 - 9 + 6)^4 \\
 & := (8 + 629 - 7 + 2 - 8 - 7 - 69 - 6)^4 \\
 & := (-8 + 629 - 7 + 2 + 8 - 7 - 69 - 6)^4 \\
 & := (-86 - 2 - 9 - 72 + 8 + 7 + 696)^4 \\
 & := (8 - 62 - 97 - 2 - 8 + 7 + 696)^4 \\
 & := (-8 - 62 - 97 - 2 + 8 + 7 + 696)^4 \\
 & := (-8 + 6 - 2 + 9 - 72 - 87 + 696)^4 \\
 & := (86 - 297 - 2 - 8 + 769 - 6)^4 \\
 \mathbf{86617093024} & := (86 + 61 + 7 + 09 - 3 - 02 - 4)^5 \\
 & := (86 + 61 - 7 + 09 + 3 - 02 + 4)^5 \\
 & := (86 + 61 + 7 - 09 + 3 + 02 + 4)^5 \\
 & := (8 - 6 - 6 + 170 - 9 + 3 - 02 - 4)^5 \\
 & := (-8 - 6 - 6 + 170 + 9 - 3 + 02 - 4)^5 \\
 & := (-8 + 6 - 6 + 170 - 9 + 3 + 02 - 4)^5 \\
 & := (-8 - 6 + 6 + 170 - 9 + 3 + 02 - 4)^5 \\
 & := (8 - 6 - 6 + 1 + 70 + 93 - 02 - 4)^5
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 &:= (-8 + 6 - 6 + 1 + 70 + 93 + 02 - 4)^5 & &:= (-8 + 8 + 2 + 2 + 38 + 506 + 2 - 5)^4 \\
 &:= (-8 - 6 + 6 + 1 + 70 + 93 + 02 - 4)^5 & &:= (-88 - 2 + 23 - 8 - 5 + 0625)^4 \\
 &:= (86 - 6 - 17 + 093 + 02 - 4)^5 & &:= (88 - 2 - 2 - 38 + 506 - 2 - 5)^4 \\
 &:= (86 + 6 + 17 + 09 + 30 + 2 + 4)^5 & &:= (-8 - 82 + 23 - 8 - 5 + 0625)^4 \\
 &:= (-8 + 66 - 1 + 70 - 9 + 30 + 2 + 4)^5 & &:= (8 + 8 - 22 + 38 + 506 + 2 + 5)^4 \\
 &:= (-8 - 6 + 61 + 70 + 9 + 30 + 2 - 4)^5 & &:= (-8 - 8 - 2 + 23 - 85 + 0625)^4 \\
 &:= (8 + 6 + 6 + 170 - 9 - 3 - 024)^5 & &:= (-88 - 2 - 2 - 38 + 50 + 625)^4 \\
 &:= (8 - 6 - 6 + 170 + 9 + 3 - 024)^5 & &:= (-8 - 82 - 2 - 38 + 50 + 625)^4 \\
 &:= (8 + 6 + 6 + 17 + 093 + 024)^5 & &:= (882 + 238 + 50 - 625)^4 \\
 &:= (8 + 6 + 6 + 1 + 70 + 9 + 30 + 24)^5 & & \mathbf{88312980625} := (-883 + 1 + 298062 - 5)^2 \\
 &:= (86 + 6 + 17 - 09 + 30 + 24)^5 & & \mathbf{88418496375} := (-88 - 418 + 4963 - 7 + 5)^3 \\
 &:= (-86 - 6 + 1 - 70 + 9 + 302 + 4)^5 & & \mathbf{88537631993} := (885 + 376 + 3199 - 3)^3 \\
 &:= (86 - 6 + 1 + 70 + 9 - 30 + 24)^5 & & \mathbf{88656874579} := (-88 - 6 - 5 - 6 - 8 - 7 + 4579)^3 \\
 &:= (8 + 66 + 17 + 09 + 30 + 24)^5 & & &:= (-8 - 86 - 5 - 6 - 8 - 7 + 4579)^3 \\
 &:= (-8 - 66 + 1 - 70 - 9 + 302 + 4)^5 & & &:= (-8 - 8 - 6 - 5 - 6 - 87 + 4579)^3 \\
 &:= (86 + 61 + 70 - 9 - 30 - 24)^5 & & \mathbf{88873149456} := (88 + 8 - 7 - 3 - 1 - 4 + 9 + 456)^4 \\
 \mathbf{86644265625} := (-8 + 66 + 4426 - 56 + 2 - 5)^3 & & & &:= (88 - 8 + 7 - 3 + 1 - 4 + 9 + 456)^4 \\
 &:= (86 - 6 + 4426 - 56 - 25)^3 & & &:= (88 - 8 - 7 + 3 + 1 + 4 + 9 + 456)^4 \\
 \mathbf{86664294544} := (-86 - 66 - 4 + 294544)^2 & & & &:= (8 + 88 - 7 - 3 - 1 - 4 + 9 + 456)^4 \\
 &:= (-86 - 6 - 64 + 294544)^2 & & &:= (-8 + 88 + 7 - 3 + 1 - 4 + 9 + 456)^4 \\
 \mathbf{86935932801} := (869 - 3 - 5 + 9 - 328 + 01)^4 & & & &:= (-8 + 88 - 7 + 3 + 1 + 4 + 9 + 456)^4 \\
 &:= (8 + 6 - 93 + 593 + 28 + 01)^4 & & &:= (8 - 8 + 87 - 3 + 1 - 4 + 9 + 456)^4 \\
 &:= (869 - 35 - 9 - 3 - 280 + 1)^4 & & &:= (-8 + 8 + 87 - 3 + 1 - 4 + 9 + 456)^4 \\
 \mathbf{87578116096} := (-8 - 7 + 578 + 1 + 1 - 6 - 09 - 6)^4 & & & &:= (-88 - 8 + 731 + 4 - 94 - 5 + 6)^4 \\
 &:= (-8 + 7 + 5 + 7 - 81 - 1 + 609 + 6)^4 & & &:= (-8 - 88 + 731 + 4 - 94 - 5 + 6)^4 \\
 &:= (8 - 75 - 7 - 8 + 11 + 609 + 6)^4 & & &:= (-888 - 7 + 3 + 1494 - 56)^4 \\
 &:= (-8 - 75 - 7 + 8 + 11 + 609 + 6)^4 & & &:= (-8 - 887 + 3 + 1494 - 56)^4 \\
 &:= (8 - 7 - 57 + 8 - 11 + 609 - 6)^4 & & & \mathbf{88955449344} := (8 + 8 + 9 - 5 - 5 + 4493 - 44)^3 \\
 &:= (8 - 7 - 5 - 78 + 11 + 609 + 6)^4 & & & \mathbf{89075066696} := (89 + 07 + 5066 - 696)^3 \\
 &:= (-87 - 5 + 781 - 160 + 9 + 6)^4 & & & \mathbf{89254693709} := (-8 - 925 + 4693 + 709)^3 \\
 &:= (-87 + 5 + 781 + 1 - 60 - 96)^4 & & & \mathbf{89374579111} := (8 - 9 - 3 + 7 + 4579 - 111)^3 \\
 &:= (-875 - 7 + 811 + 609 + 6)^4 & & & \mathbf{89434562048} := (89 + 4345 + 6 + 20 + 4 + 8)^3 \\
 \mathbf{87824421125} := (8 - 7 + 8 - 2 + 4421 + 12 + 5)^3 & & & & &:= (8 + 9 + 4345 + 62 + 048)^3 \\
 &:= (878 + 2442 + 1125)^3 & & & &:= (-8 + 9 - 43 + 4562 - 048)^3 \\
 \mathbf{87943022623} := (87 - 9 + 4302 + 2 + 62 + 3)^3 & & & & \mathbf{89466096875} := (89 - 4 + 6 - 6 + 09 - 6 - 8 + 75)^5 \\
 &:= (87 + 9 + 4302 + 26 + 23)^3 & & & &:= (89 - 4 - 6 + 6 + 09 - 6 - 8 + 75)^5 \\
 &:= (8 + 794 + 3022 + 623)^3 & & & &:= (89 - 4 - 6 - 6 + 09 + 6 - 8 + 75)^5 \\
 \mathbf{88223850625} := (8 - 8 + 2 + 2 + 38 + 506 + 2 - 5)^4 & & & & &:= (8 + 94 + 66 - 09 + 6 - 8 - 7 + 5)^5
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 &:= (-8 + 94 + 66 - 09 + 6 + 8 - 7 + 5)^5 \\
 &:= (8 + 94 - 6 + 60 + 9 - 6 + 8 - 7 - 5)^5 \\
 &:= (8 + 94 + 6 + 60 - 9 + 6 - 8 - 7 + 5)^5 \\
 &:= (-8 + 94 + 6 + 60 - 9 + 6 + 8 - 7 + 5)^5 \\
 &:= (8 + 94 - 6 - 6 + 09 + 68 - 7 - 5)^5 \\
 &:= (-8 + 94 + 6 + 6 - 09 + 68 - 7 + 5)^5 \\
 &:= (8 + 9 + 46 + 6 + 096 - 8 - 7 + 5)^5 \\
 &:= (-8 + 9 + 46 + 6 + 096 + 8 - 7 + 5)^5 \\
 &:= (8 - 9 + 46 - 6 + 096 + 8 + 7 + 5)^5 \\
 &:= (8 + 9 + 46 + 6 + 09 - 6 + 8 + 75)^5 \\
 &:= (8 + 9 + 46 - 6 + 09 + 6 + 8 + 75)^5 \\
 &:= (8 + 9 - 4 + 66 + 096 - 8 - 7 - 5)^5 \\
 &:= (-8 + 9 - 4 + 66 + 096 + 8 - 7 - 5)^5 \\
 &:= (8 - 9 + 4 + 66 + 096 - 8 - 7 + 5)^5 \\
 &:= (-8 - 9 + 4 + 66 + 096 + 8 - 7 + 5)^5 \\
 &:= (8 + 9 + 4 + 66 - 09 - 6 + 8 + 75)^5 \\
 &:= (8 - 9 + 4 + 66 + 09 - 6 + 8 + 75)^5 \\
 &:= (8 + 9 - 4 + 6 + 60 + 96 - 8 - 7 - 5)^5 \\
 &:= (-8 + 9 - 4 + 6 + 60 + 96 + 8 - 7 - 5)^5 \\
 &:= (8 - 9 - 4 - 6 + 60 + 96 + 8 + 7 - 5)^5 \\
 &:= (8 - 9 + 4 + 6 + 60 + 96 - 8 - 7 + 5)^5 \\
 &:= (-8 - 9 + 4 + 6 + 60 + 96 + 8 - 7 + 5)^5 \\
 &:= (8 + 9 + 4 + 6 + 60 - 9 - 6 + 8 + 75)^5 \\
 &:= (8 - 9 + 4 + 6 + 60 + 9 - 6 + 8 + 75)^5 \\
 &:= (8 + 9 + 4 - 6 + 60 - 9 + 6 + 8 + 75)^5 \\
 &:= (8 - 9 + 4 - 6 + 60 + 9 + 6 + 8 + 75)^5 \\
 &:= (-8 - 9 - 4 - 6 - 6 + 096 + 87 + 5)^5 \\
 &:= (8 + 9 + 4 + 6 - 6 - 09 + 68 + 75)^5 \\
 &:= (8 + 9 + 4 - 6 + 6 - 09 + 68 + 75)^5 \\
 &:= (8 - 9 + 4 + 6 - 6 + 09 + 68 + 75)^5 \\
 &:= (8 - 9 + 4 - 6 + 6 + 09 + 68 + 75)^5 \\
 &:= (89 - 46 + 6 + 096 + 8 + 7 - 5)^5 \\
 &:= (89 + 4 + 6 - 60 + 96 + 8 + 7 + 5)^5 \\
 &:= (8 + 94 + 6 - 60 + 9 + 6 + 87 + 5)^5 \\
 &:= (8 + 9 - 46 + 6 + 096 + 87 - 5)^5 \\
 &:= (8 + 9 + 4 + 6 - 60 + 96 + 87 + 5)^5 \\
 &:= (89 - 46 + 60 - 9 - 6 - 8 + 75)^5 \\
 &:= (89 + 46 - 60 - 9 + 6 + 8 + 75)^5
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 &:= (89 + 46 + 6 + 096 - 87 + 5)^5 \\
 &:= (89 - 4 + 66 + 096 - 87 - 5)^5 \\
 &:= (89 + 4 + 66 - 096 + 87 + 5)^5 \\
 &:= (89 - 4 + 6 + 60 + 96 - 87 - 5)^5 \\
 &:= (89 + 4 + 6 + 60 - 96 + 87 + 5)^5 \\
 &:= (89 - 4 - 6 + 60 + 9 - 68 + 75)^5 \\
 &:= (8 + 94 + 66 - 096 + 8 + 75)^5 \\
 &:= (8 + 94 + 6 + 60 - 96 + 8 + 75)^5 \\
 &:= (8 + 9 + 46 - 60 + 9 + 68 + 75)^5 \\
 &:= (894 - 660 - 9 - 68 - 7 + 5)^5 \\
 &:= (894 - 660 + 9 - 6 - 87 + 5)^5 \\
 &:= (894 - 66 + 09 - 687 + 5)^5 \\
 &:= (894 - 6 - 60 + 9 - 687 + 5)^5 \\
 &89494571817 := (-89 - 4 + 9 + 4571 - 8 + 1 - 7)^3 \\
 &89526025681 := (8 + 9 + 526 + 02 + 5 + 6 - 8 - 1)^4 \\
 &:= (8 + 9 + 526 - 02 + 5 - 6 + 8 - 1)^4 \\
 &:= (-8 + 9 + 526 + 02 + 5 + 6 + 8 - 1)^4 \\
 &:= (8 - 9 + 526 + 02 + 5 + 6 + 8 + 1)^4 \\
 &:= (-8 - 9 - 5 - 2 + 6 - 02 + 568 - 1)^4 \\
 &:= (-8 - 9 + 5 - 2 - 6 - 02 + 568 + 1)^4 \\
 &:= (8 - 9 + 526 + 025 + 6 - 8 - 1)^4 \\
 &:= (-8 - 9 + 526 + 025 + 6 + 8 - 1)^4 \\
 &:= (8 + 9 - 52 + 602 - 5 - 6 - 8 - 1)^4 \\
 &:= (-8 + 9 - 52 + 602 - 5 - 6 + 8 - 1)^4 \\
 &:= (8 - 9 - 52 + 602 - 5 - 6 + 8 + 1)^4 \\
 &:= (8 - 9 + 5 - 26 + 02 + 568 - 1)^4 \\
 &:= (-8 + 9 + 5 - 26 - 02 + 568 + 1)^4 \\
 &:= (8 + 9 - 5 - 2 + 602 - 56 - 8 - 1)^4 \\
 &:= (-8 + 9 - 5 - 2 + 602 - 56 + 8 - 1)^4 \\
 &:= (-8 + 9 + 5 + 2 + 602 - 56 - 8 + 1)^4 \\
 &:= (8 - 9 - 5 - 2 + 602 - 56 + 8 + 1)^4 \\
 &:= (89 + 526 + 02 + 5 + 6 - 81)^4 \\
 &:= (-89 + 52 + 602 - 5 - 6 - 8 + 1)^4 \\
 &:= (-89 + 5 + 2 + 60 + 2 + 568 - 1)^4 \\
 &:= (8 + 9 + 5 + 260 + 256 + 8 + 1)^4 \\
 &:= (89 - 52 + 602 - 5 - 6 - 81)^4 \\
 &:= (89 - 5 - 2 + 602 - 56 - 81)^4 \\
 &:= (-8 + 952 - 60 - 256 - 81)^4
 \end{aligned}$$

89554608424 := (-89 - 55 + 4608 + 4 + 2 + 4) ³	:= (9 - 04 - 5 - 8 - 3 + 8 + 2 - 1 + 69) ⁶
89674762176 := (-89 + 6747 - 6 - 2176) ³	:= (-9 + 04 + 5 - 8 - 3 + 8 + 2 - 1 + 69) ⁶
89734879333 := (897 + 3487 + 93 + 3 - 3) ³	:= (9 + 04 + 5 - 8 - 3 - 8 - 2 + 1 + 69) ⁶
:= (897 + 3487 + 93 - 3 + 3) ³	:= (9 + 04 - 5 - 8 + 3 - 8 + 2 + 1 + 69) ⁶
89943009025 := (-8 - 994 + 300902 + 5) ²	:= (-9 - 04 + 5 + 8 + 3 - 8 + 2 + 1 + 69) ⁶
90182492416 := (90 - 1 + 8 + 24 + 9 + 2 + 416) ⁴	:= (-9 - 04 - 5 + 8 - 3 + 8 + 2 + 1 + 69) ⁶
:= (90 + 1 - 8 + 2 + 49 - 2 + 416) ⁴	:= (-9 - 04 + 5 - 8 + 3 + 8 + 2 + 1 + 69) ⁶
:= (90 + 1 - 8 - 2 + 49 + 2 + 416) ⁴	:= (90 + 4 + 5 + 8 - 38 + 2 - 1 + 6 - 9) ⁶
:= (9 - 01 + 8 + 24 + 92 + 416) ⁴	:= (90 - 4 + 5 + 8 - 38 + 2 + 1 - 6 + 9) ⁶
:= (90 + 1 - 82 + 492 + 41 + 6) ⁴	:= (90 - 4 - 5 + 8 - 38 + 2 - 1 + 6 + 9) ⁶
90458382169 := (9 + 045 + 8 + 3 + 8 - 2 - 1 + 6 - 9) ⁶	:= (90 + 4 + 5 - 8 - 38 - 2 + 1 + 6 + 9) ⁶
:= (9 + 045 + 8 - 3 + 8 + 2 + 1 + 6 - 9) ⁶	:= (90 - 4 + 5 + 8 + 3 - 8 - 2 - 16 - 9) ⁶
:= (9 + 045 + 8 - 3 + 8 - 2 - 1 - 6 + 9) ⁶	:= (90 - 4 - 5 + 8 - 3 + 8 - 2 - 16 - 9) ⁶
:= (-9 + 045 + 8 + 3 + 8 - 2 - 1 + 6 + 9) ⁶	:= (90 - 4 + 5 - 8 + 3 + 8 - 2 - 16 - 9) ⁶
:= (9 + 045 + 8 - 3 - 8 + 2 - 1 + 6 + 9) ⁶	:= (90 - 4 - 5 - 8 - 3 - 8 - 2 + 16 - 9) ⁶
:= (9 + 045 - 8 - 3 + 8 + 2 - 1 + 6 + 9) ⁶	:= (90 + 4 - 5 - 8 + 3 - 8 - 2 - 16 + 9) ⁶
:= (-9 + 045 + 8 - 3 + 8 + 2 + 1 + 6 + 9) ⁶	:= (90 - 4 + 5 - 8 - 3 - 8 + 2 - 16 + 9) ⁶
:= (9 - 04 + 5 + 83 - 8 - 2 - 1 - 6 - 9) ⁶	:= (9 - 045 + 83 + 8 - 2 - 1 + 6 + 9) ⁶
:= (-9 + 04 - 5 + 83 + 8 + 2 - 1 - 6 - 9) ⁶	:= (9 - 045 + 8 - 3 + 82 + 1 + 6 + 9) ⁶
:= (9 + 04 - 5 + 83 - 8 - 2 + 1 - 6 - 9) ⁶	:= (-9 + 045 + 8 - 3 + 8 + 21 + 6 - 9) ⁶
:= (-9 - 04 + 5 + 83 + 8 - 2 + 1 - 6 - 9) ⁶	:= (9 + 045 + 8 + 3 + 8 - 21 + 6 + 9) ⁶
:= (-9 - 04 - 5 + 83 + 8 - 2 - 1 + 6 - 9) ⁶	:= (-9 - 04 + 58 + 38 - 2 + 1 - 6 - 9) ⁶
:= (-9 - 04 + 5 + 83 - 8 + 2 + 1 + 6 - 9) ⁶	:= (9 - 04 + 58 + 3 - 8 + 2 + 16 - 9) ⁶
:= (-9 - 04 + 5 + 83 - 8 - 2 - 1 - 6 + 9) ⁶	:= (-9 + 04 + 58 - 3 + 8 + 2 + 16 - 9) ⁶
:= (-9 + 04 - 5 + 83 - 8 - 2 + 1 - 6 + 9) ⁶	:= (9 + 04 + 58 - 3 + 8 - 2 - 16 + 9) ⁶
:= (-9 + 04 - 5 + 8 + 3 + 82 - 1 - 6 - 9) ⁶	:= (-9 - 04 + 58 + 3 - 8 + 2 + 16 + 9) ⁶
:= (9 - 04 + 5 - 8 - 3 + 82 + 1 - 6 - 9) ⁶	:= (9 - 04 - 5 + 83 + 8 - 21 + 6 - 9) ⁶
:= (9 - 04 - 5 - 8 - 3 + 82 - 1 + 6 - 9) ⁶	:= (-9 + 04 + 5 + 83 + 8 - 21 + 6 - 9) ⁶
:= (-9 + 04 + 5 - 8 - 3 + 82 - 1 + 6 - 9) ⁶	:= (9 - 04 + 5 + 83 - 8 - 21 - 6 + 9) ⁶
:= (-9 - 04 - 5 + 8 - 3 + 82 + 1 + 6 - 9) ⁶	:= (-9 - 04 - 5 + 83 + 8 - 21 + 6 + 9) ⁶
:= (-9 - 04 + 5 - 8 + 3 + 82 + 1 + 6 - 9) ⁶	:= (9 - 04 + 5 - 8 + 38 + 2 + 16 + 9) ⁶
:= (-9 - 04 + 5 - 8 - 3 + 82 + 1 - 6 + 9) ⁶	:= (9 - 04 - 5 + 8 + 3 + 8 - 21 + 69) ⁶
:= (-9 - 04 - 5 - 8 - 3 + 82 - 1 + 6 + 9) ⁶	:= (-9 + 04 + 5 + 8 + 3 + 8 - 21 + 69) ⁶
:= (9 + 04 + 5 + 8 - 3 + 8 + 21 + 6 + 9) ⁶	:= (-9 + 04 - 5 - 8 + 3 - 8 + 21 + 69) ⁶
:= (-9 - 04 - 5 + 8 + 3 + 8 - 2 - 1 + 69) ⁶	:= (90 - 45 + 8 - 3 + 8 + 2 + 16 - 9) ⁶
:= (9 - 04 - 5 + 8 - 3 - 8 + 2 - 1 + 69) ⁶	:= (90 - 4 + 58 + 3 - 82 - 1 - 6 + 9) ⁶
:= (-9 + 04 + 5 + 8 - 3 - 8 + 2 - 1 + 69) ⁶	:= (-90 + 4 + 58 - 3 + 82 + 1 + 6 + 9) ⁶
:= (9 - 04 + 5 - 8 + 3 - 8 + 2 - 1 + 69) ⁶	:= (90 + 4 - 58 + 3 - 8 + 21 + 6 + 9) ⁶

$$\begin{aligned} &:= (90 - 4 + 58 + 3 - 8 - 2 - 1 - 69)^6 \\ &:= (90 - 4 + 58 - 3 - 8 + 2 + 1 - 69)^6 \\ &:= (90 - 4 + 5 + 8 - 38 + 21 - 6 - 9)^6 \\ &:= (90 + 4 - 5 - 8 - 38 + 21 - 6 + 9)^6 \\ &:= (90 + 4 - 5 + 8 + 38 + 2 - 1 - 69)^6 \\ &:= (90 - 4 + 5 + 8 + 38 - 2 + 1 - 69)^6 \\ &:= (-90 + 4 + 5 - 8 - 3 - 8 - 2 + 169)^6 \\ &:= (-90 + 4 - 5 - 8 + 3 - 8 + 2 + 169)^6 \\ &:= (9 + 045 - 83 + 82 - 1 + 6 + 9)^6 \\ &:= (9 - 045 + 8 - 3 + 8 + 21 + 69)^6 \\ &:= (-9 + 04 + 58 + 38 - 21 + 6 - 9)^6 \\ &:= (9 - 04 - 5 - 83 + 82 - 1 + 69)^6 \\ &:= (-9 + 04 + 5 - 83 + 82 - 1 + 69)^6 \\ &:= (904 + 5 - 838 - 2 + 1 + 6 - 9)^6 \\ &:= (904 - 5 - 838 + 2 + 1 - 6 + 9)^6 \\ &:= (-90 + 4583 + 8 + 2 + 1 - 6 - 9)^3 \\ &:= (-90 + 4583 - 8 + 2 - 1 - 6 + 9)^3 \\ &:= (90 + 45 - 83 - 8 - 2 + 16 + 9)^6 \\ &:= (90 - 45 + 8 + 38 - 21 + 6 - 9)^6 \\ &:= (-90 + 45 + 8 + 38 - 2 - 1 + 69)^6 \\ &:= (90 - 45 - 8 - 38 - 2 + 1 + 69)^6 \\ &:= (90 + 45 - 8 - 3 - 82 + 16 + 9)^6 \\ &:= (-90 + 45 + 8 - 3 + 82 + 16 + 9)^6 \\ &:= (90 + 4 + 58 - 3 + 8 - 21 - 69)^6 \\ &:= (-90 + 4 + 58 - 3 + 8 + 21 + 69)^6 \\ &:= (90 - 4 + 5 + 83 - 82 - 16 - 9)^6 \\ &:= (-90 + 4 - 5 + 83 + 82 - 16 + 9)^6 \\ &:= (-9 - 045 - 8 - 38 - 2 + 169)^6 \\ &:= (904 - 5 - 838 + 21 - 6 - 9)^6 \\ \mathbf{90639863488} &:= (9 + 06 + 3986 + 3 + 488)^3 \\ &:= (9 + 06 + 3 + 986 + 3488)^3 \\ &:= (906 + 3 + 9 + 86 + 3488)^3 \\ \mathbf{90842562801} &:= (9 - 084 + 2 - 5 + 628 - 01)^4 \\ &:= (-90 + 84 + 2 + 562 - 8 - 01)^4 \\ &:= (-90 - 8 + 4 + 2 + 562 + 80 - 1)^4 \\ &:= (-9 - 08 + 425 + 62 + 80 - 1)^4 \\ &:= (90 - 84 - 256 - 2 + 801)^4 \\ \mathbf{91064263499} &:= (910 + 64 + 26 + 3499)^3 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{91185763501} &:= (911 + 8 + 5 + 76 + 3501)^3 \\ \mathbf{91489986216} &:= (-91 + 4899 - 86 - 216)^3 \\ \mathbf{91506250000} &:= (-9 + 1 + 506 + 2 + 50 + 000)^4 \\ &:= (9 - 1 + 50 - 6 - 2 + 500 + 00)^4 \\ &:= (-9 + 1 + 50 + 6 + 2 + 500 + 00)^4 \\ \mathbf{91611864512} &:= (-9 - 1 + 6 - 1 - 1 + 8 - 6 + 4512)^3 \\ &:= (-9 + 1 + 6 + 1 - 1 - 8 + 6 + 4512)^3 \\ &:= (-9 + 1 + 6 - 1 + 1 - 8 + 6 + 4512)^3 \\ &:= (-9 - 1 + 6 + 1 + 1 - 8 + 6 + 4512)^3 \\ &:= (-9 - 1 - 6 - 1 - 1 + 8 + 6 + 4512)^3 \\ &:= (9 - 16 - 11 + 8 + 6 + 4512)^3 \\ &:= (-9 + 16 + 1 - 18 + 6 + 4512)^3 \\ \mathbf{91672844229} &:= (91 + 6 - 7 - 2 + 8 + 4422 - 9)^3 \\ &:= (9 + 1 + 6 + 72 + 8 + 4422 - 9)^3 \\ &:= (9 - 1 + 6 + 72 - 8 + 4422 + 9)^3 \\ &:= (-9 + 1 + 6 + 72 + 8 + 4422 + 9)^3 \\ \mathbf{91819302289} &:= (-91 + 819 + 302289)^2 \\ \mathbf{91855945728} &:= (9 + 1 - 8 + 5 - 59 + 4572 - 8)^3 \\ \mathbf{92100460096} &:= (9 + 2 + 1 + 004600 - 96)^3 \\ &:= (-9 + 21 + 004600 - 96)^3 \\ \mathbf{92173567201} &:= (9 - 2 - 17 - 3 + 567 - 2 - 01)^4 \\ &:= (-9 - 2 + 17 - 3 + 567 - 20 + 1)^4 \\ &:= (9 - 2 + 1 - 7 + 356 - 7 + 201)^4 \\ &:= (-9 + 2 + 1 + 7 + 356 - 7 + 201)^4 \\ &:= (-9 + 2 + 1 - 7 + 356 + 7 + 201)^4 \\ &:= (-92 - 17 - 3 - 56 + 720 - 1)^4 \\ &:= (9 + 21 + 735 - 6 - 7 - 201)^4 \\ &:= (921 - 7 + 356 - 720 + 1)^4 \\ &:= (921 - 7 + 3 - 567 + 201)^4 \\ \mathbf{92389579776} &:= (92 + 38 + 9 - 5 + 7 + 9 + 7 - 7 + 6)^5 \\ &:= (92 + 38 + 9 - 5 + 7 + 9 - 7 + 7 + 6)^5 \\ &:= (92 + 38 + 9 - 5 - 7 + 9 + 7 + 7 + 6)^5 \\ &:= (92 - 3 + 8 + 95 - 7 - 9 - 7 - 7 - 6)^5 \\ &:= (92 + 3 - 8 + 9 + 57 + 9 + 7 - 7 - 6)^5 \\ &:= (92 + 3 - 8 + 9 + 57 + 9 - 7 + 7 - 6)^5 \\ &:= (92 - 3 + 8 - 9 + 57 - 9 + 7 + 7 + 6)^5 \\ &:= (92 - 3 + 8 - 9 - 5 + 79 + 7 - 7 - 6)^5 \\ &:= (92 + 3 - 8 - 9 + 5 + 79 + 7 - 7 - 6)^5 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} &:= (92 - 3 + 8 - 9 - 5 + 79 - 7 + 7 - 6)^5 & &:= (9 - 2 - 3 + 8 - 9 + 5 + 79 - 7 + 76)^5 \\ &:= (92 + 3 - 8 - 9 + 5 + 79 - 7 + 7 - 6)^5 & &:= (-9 - 2 - 3 + 8 + 9 + 5 + 79 - 7 + 76)^5 \\ &:= (92 - 3 - 8 + 9 - 5 + 79 - 7 - 7 + 6)^5 & &:= (-9 + 2 - 3 + 8 - 9 + 5 + 79 + 7 + 76)^5 \\ &:= (92 - 3 - 8 - 9 - 5 - 7 + 97 - 7 + 6)^5 & &:= (-9 + 2 + 3 + 8 - 9 - 5 - 7 + 97 + 76)^5 \\ &:= (92 - 3 + 8 + 9 - 5 - 7 - 9 + 77 - 6)^5 & &:= (-9 - 2 - 3 + 8 - 9 + 5 - 7 + 97 + 76)^5 \\ &:= (92 + 3 - 8 + 9 + 5 - 7 - 9 + 77 - 6)^5 & &:= (92 + 3 + 89 - 57 + 9 + 7 + 7 + 6)^5 \\ &:= (92 - 3 + 8 - 9 - 5 - 7 + 9 + 77 - 6)^5 & &:= (9 + 238 - 95 + 7 - 9 + 7 - 7 + 6)^5 \\ &:= (92 + 3 - 8 - 9 + 5 - 7 + 9 + 77 - 6)^5 & &:= (-9 + 238 - 95 + 7 + 9 + 7 - 7 + 6)^5 \\ &:= (92 + 3 + 8 - 9 - 5 - 7 - 9 + 77 + 6)^5 & &:= (9 + 238 - 95 + 7 - 9 - 7 + 7 + 6)^5 \\ &:= (92 + 3 + 8 - 9 - 5 + 7 - 9 - 7 + 76)^5 & &:= (-9 + 238 - 95 + 7 + 9 - 7 + 7 + 6)^5 \\ &:= (92 - 3 - 8 + 9 - 5 - 7 + 9 - 7 + 76)^5 & &:= (9 + 238 - 95 - 7 - 9 + 7 + 7 + 6)^5 \\ &:= (92 + 3 + 8 - 9 - 5 - 7 - 9 + 7 + 76)^5 & &:= (-9 + 238 - 95 - 7 + 9 + 7 + 7 + 6)^5 \\ &:= (9 + 2 + 38 + 9 - 5 + 7 + 97 - 7 + 6)^5 & &:= (9 + 238 - 9 + 5 - 79 - 7 - 7 + 6)^5 \\ &:= (9 + 2 + 38 + 9 - 5 - 7 + 97 + 7 + 6)^5 & &:= (-9 + 238 + 9 + 5 - 79 - 7 - 7 + 6)^5 \\ &:= (9 - 2 + 3 - 8 + 95 + 79 - 7 - 7 - 6)^5 & &:= (-9 + 238 - 9 - 5 - 79 + 7 + 7 + 6)^5 \\ &:= (-9 + 2 + 3 - 8 + 95 + 79 + 7 - 7 - 6)^5 & &:= (9 + 238 + 9 + 5 - 7 - 97 - 7 + 6)^5 \\ &:= (-9 + 2 + 3 - 8 + 95 + 79 - 7 + 7 - 6)^5 & &:= (9 + 238 - 9 - 5 + 7 - 97 + 7 + 6)^5 \\ &:= (-9 - 2 + 3 - 8 + 95 - 7 + 97 - 7 - 6)^5 & &:= (-9 + 238 + 9 - 5 + 7 - 97 + 7 + 6)^5 \\ &:= (9 + 2 + 3 - 8 + 95 - 7 - 9 + 77 - 6)^5 & &:= (9 + 238 - 9 + 5 - 7 - 9 - 77 + 6)^5 \\ &:= (-9 + 2 + 3 - 8 + 95 - 7 + 9 + 77 - 6)^5 & &:= (-9 + 238 + 9 + 5 - 7 - 9 - 77 + 6)^5 \\ &:= (-9 - 2 - 3 + 8 + 95 - 7 - 9 + 77 + 6)^5 & &:= (-9 + 238 - 9 + 5 - 7 + 9 - 77 + 6)^5 \\ &:= (-9 - 2 - 3 + 8 + 95 + 7 - 9 - 7 + 76)^5 & &:= (-9 - 23 + 8 + 95 + 79 + 7 - 7 + 6)^5 \\ &:= (-9 - 2 - 3 + 8 + 95 - 7 - 9 + 7 + 76)^5 & &:= (-9 - 23 + 8 + 95 + 79 - 7 + 7 + 6)^5 \\ &:= (9 + 2 + 3 - 8 + 9 + 57 + 97 - 7 - 6)^5 & &:= (-9 + 23 - 8 + 95 - 7 - 9 + 77 - 6)^5 \\ &:= (9 - 2 - 3 + 8 - 9 + 57 + 97 - 7 + 6)^5 & &:= (9 - 23 + 8 + 95 - 7 - 9 + 77 + 6)^5 \\ &:= (-9 - 2 - 3 + 8 + 9 + 57 + 97 - 7 + 6)^5 & &:= (-9 - 23 + 8 + 95 - 7 + 9 + 77 + 6)^5 \\ &:= (-9 + 2 - 3 + 8 - 9 + 57 + 97 + 7 + 6)^5 & &:= (9 - 23 + 8 + 95 + 7 - 9 - 7 + 76)^5 \\ &:= (9 + 2 - 3 + 8 + 9 + 57 - 9 + 77 + 6)^5 & &:= (-9 - 23 + 8 + 95 + 7 + 9 - 7 + 76)^5 \\ &:= (9 + 2 - 3 + 8 - 9 + 57 + 9 + 77 + 6)^5 & &:= (9 - 23 + 8 + 95 - 7 - 9 + 7 + 76)^5 \\ &:= (-9 + 2 - 3 + 8 + 9 + 57 + 9 + 77 + 6)^5 & &:= (-9 - 23 + 8 + 95 - 7 + 9 + 7 + 76)^5 \\ &:= (9 - 2 - 3 + 8 + 9 + 57 + 9 - 7 + 76)^5 & &:= (9 + 23 - 8 - 9 + 57 + 97 - 7 - 6)^5 \\ &:= (9 + 2 - 3 + 8 + 9 + 57 - 9 + 7 + 76)^5 & &:= (-9 + 23 - 8 + 9 + 57 + 97 - 7 - 6)^5 \\ &:= (9 + 2 - 3 + 8 - 9 + 57 + 9 + 7 + 76)^5 & &:= (9 - 23 + 8 + 9 + 57 + 97 - 7 + 6)^5 \\ &:= (-9 + 2 - 3 + 8 + 9 + 57 + 9 + 7 + 76)^5 & &:= (-9 + 23 + 8 - 9 - 5 + 79 - 7 + 76)^5 \\ &:= (9 - 2 + 3 - 8 + 9 - 5 + 79 + 77 - 6)^5 & &:= (9 - 23 + 8 + 9 + 5 + 79 - 7 + 76)^5 \\ &:= (-9 + 2 - 3 + 8 - 9 + 5 + 79 + 77 + 6)^5 & &:= (9 - 23 + 8 - 9 + 5 - 7 + 97 + 76)^5 \\ &:= (9 + 2 + 3 + 8 - 9 - 5 + 79 - 7 + 76)^5 & &:= (-9 - 23 + 8 + 9 + 5 - 7 + 97 + 76)^5 \\ &:= (-9 + 2 + 3 + 8 + 9 - 5 + 79 - 7 + 76)^5 & &:= (9 + 2 + 3 + 89 - 57 + 97 + 7 + 6)^5 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 &:= (92 + 38 + 95 - 7 + 9 - 77 + 6)^5 & &:= (92 - 8 + 4 + 4 + 527 - 61 - 6)^4 \\
 &:= (92 + 38 + 9 - 57 - 9 + 77 + 6)^5 & &:= (9 - 28 + 4 - 4 - 52 + 7 + 616)^4 \\
 &:= (92 + 38 - 9 - 57 + 9 + 77 + 6)^5 & &:= (9 - 28 - 4 + 4 - 52 + 7 + 616)^4 \\
 &:= (92 + 38 + 9 - 57 - 9 + 7 + 76)^5 & &:= (9 + 2 - 8 + 44 + 527 - 6 - 16)^4 \\
 &:= (92 + 38 - 9 - 57 + 9 + 7 + 76)^5 & &:= (928 - 445 - 2 + 76 + 1 - 6)^4 \\
 &:= (92 + 3 + 8 - 95 + 79 - 7 + 76)^5 & &:= (9 + 284 + 4 - 5 + 276 - 16)^4 \\
 &:= (-92 - 3 + 8 + 95 + 79 - 7 + 76)^5 & &:= (92 - 84 + 452 + 76 + 16)^4 \\
 &:= (92 + 3 - 8 - 9 + 57 + 97 - 76)^5 & &:= (92 - 84 - 45 - 27 + 616)^4 \\
 &:= (-9 + 23 + 89 - 57 + 97 + 7 + 6)^5 & & \mathbf{92982304900} := (9 + 2 + 9 + 8 + 2 + 304900)^2 \\
 &:= (9 + 23 + 89 - 57 + 9 + 77 + 6)^5 & & := (-9 + 29 + 8 + 2 + 304900)^2 \\
 &:= (9 + 23 + 89 - 57 + 9 + 7 + 76)^5 & & \mathbf{93048791521} := (9 + 304879 + 152 - 1)^2 \\
 &:= (9 + 2 + 38 - 9 - 57 + 97 + 76)^5 & & \mathbf{93144487437} := (93 - 1 + 4448 + 7 - 4 - 3 - 7)^3 \\
 &:= (-9 + 2 + 38 + 9 - 57 + 97 + 76)^5 & & := (93 - 1 + 4448 - 7 + 4 + 3 - 7)^3 \\
 &:= (-9 - 2 + 3 - 8 + 957 - 9 - 776)^5 & & := (93 - 1 + 4448 - 7 - 4 - 3 + 7)^3 \\
 &:= (-923 + 8 + 95 - 7 + 977 + 6)^5 & & := (9 - 3 + 1 + 4448 + 74 - 3 + 7)^3 \\
 &:= (-92 + 389 - 57 - 97 + 7 + 6)^5 & & := (93 - 1 + 4 + 4487 - 43 - 7)^3 \\
 &:= (9 + 238 - 95 - 79 + 77 + 6)^5 & & := (93 - 14 + 4487 + 4 - 37)^3 \\
 &:= (9 + 238 - 95 - 79 + 7 + 76)^5 & & \mathbf{93329542656} := (9 + 3329 + 542 + 656)^3 \\
 &:= (92 + 38 - 957 + 977 + 6)^5 & & \mathbf{93453048872} := (-93 + 4530 + 4 + 88 + 7 + 2)^3 \\
 \mathbf{92468044648} &:= (-92 - 46 + 8 + 04 + 4648)^3 & & := (93 + 4530 - 4 + 8 - 87 - 2)^3 \\
 &:= (9246 - 80 + 4 - 4648)^3 & & := (-93 + 4530 + 4 + 8 + 87 + 2)^3 \\
 &:= (-924 - 6 + 804 + 4648)^3 & & := (-9 - 345 + 3 + 04887 + 2)^3 \\
 \mathbf{92529403667} &:= (925 - 29 - 40 + 3667)^3 & & := (-9 - 3 + 4530 + 4 + 88 - 72)^3 \\
 \mathbf{92713643576} &:= (927 + 13 + 6 + 4 + 3576)^3 & & \mathbf{93519144481} := (9 + 3 + 519 + 1 + 4 + 4 + 4 + 8 + 1)^4 \\
 \mathbf{92844527616} &:= (92 + 8 + 4 + 452 + 7 - 6 + 1 - 6)^4 & & := (-9 + 3 + 519 + 1 + 44 + 4 - 8 - 1)^4 \\
 &:= (92 + 8 - 4 + 452 - 7 + 6 - 1 + 6)^4 & & := (-9 - 3 + 519 - 1 + 44 - 4 + 8 - 1)^4 \\
 &:= (92 - 8 - 4 + 452 + 7 + 6 + 1 + 6)^4 & & := (-9 + 3 + 519 - 1 + 44 + 4 - 8 + 1)^4 \\
 &:= (9 - 2 + 8 + 4 + 452 + 76 - 1 + 6)^4 & & := (-9 + 3 + 519 + 1 + 4 + 44 - 8 - 1)^4 \\
 &:= (9 - 2 + 8 + 4 - 4 + 527 - 6 + 16)^4 & & := (-9 - 3 + 519 - 1 - 4 + 44 + 8 - 1)^4 \\
 &:= (9 - 2 + 8 - 4 + 4 + 527 - 6 + 16)^4 & & := (-9 + 3 + 519 - 1 + 4 + 44 - 8 + 1)^4 \\
 &:= (9 + 2 - 8 + 4 - 4 + 527 + 6 + 16)^4 & & := (-9 + 3 + 519 + 1 - 4 - 4 + 48 - 1)^4 \\
 &:= (9 + 2 - 8 - 4 + 4 + 527 + 6 + 16)^4 & & := (-9 - 3 + 519 - 1 + 4 - 4 + 48 - 1)^4 \\
 &:= (9 + 2 - 8 - 4 - 4 - 52 - 7 + 616)^4 & & := (-9 - 3 + 519 - 1 - 4 + 4 + 48 - 1)^4 \\
 &:= (-9 - 2 - 8 + 4 - 4 - 52 + 7 + 616)^4 & & := (-9 + 3 + 519 - 1 - 4 - 4 + 48 + 1)^4 \\
 &:= (-9 - 2 - 8 - 4 + 4 - 52 + 7 + 616)^4 & & := (9 + 3 + 5 + 1 + 9 + 1 + 444 + 81)^4 \\
 &:= (92 - 84 + 4 + 527 + 6 + 1 + 6)^4 & & := (9 + 3 + 5 + 1 + 9 + 1 + 44 + 481)^4 \\
 &:= (-92 - 8 - 4 + 45 + 2 - 7 + 616)^4 & & := (93 + 5 + 19 + 1 + 444 - 8 - 1)^4 \\
 &:= (92 + 8 - 4 - 4 + 527 - 61 - 6)^4 & & := (93 + 5 + 19 - 1 + 444 - 8 + 1)^4
 \end{aligned}$$

$:= (93 - 5 + 19 + 1 - 4 + 448 + 1)^4$	$:= (9 + 4 + 14 + 3 + 1 - 7 - 8 - 8 + 2 - 7)^{23}$
$:= (93 + 5 - 19 + 1 - 4 - 4 + 481)^4$	$:= (9 - 4 + 14 - 3 + 1 + 7 - 8 - 8 + 2 - 7)^{23}$
$:= (93 + 5 + 1 - 9 + 14 + 448 + 1)^4$	$:= (9 - 4 + 14 - 3 - 1 - 7 + 8 - 8 + 2 - 7)^{23}$
$:= (93 + 5 + 1 - 9 - 14 - 4 + 481)^4$	$:= (9 + 4 - 14 + 3 - 1 + 7 + 8 - 8 + 2 - 7)^{23}$
$:= (-9 - 351 + 914 + 4 + 4 - 8 - 1)^4$	$:= (9 - 4 + 14 - 3 - 1 - 7 - 8 + 8 + 2 - 7)^{23}$
$:= (-9 - 351 + 914 - 4 - 4 + 8 - 1)^4$	$:= (9 + 4 - 14 + 3 - 1 + 7 - 8 + 8 + 2 - 7)^{23}$
$:= (9 + 35 + 19 + 1 + 4 + 4 + 481)^4$	$:= (-9 - 4 + 14 - 3 + 1 - 7 + 8 + 8 + 2 - 7)^{23}$
$:= (-9 + 35 + 1 + 91 + 444 - 8 - 1)^4$	$:= (-9 + 4 - 14 + 3 + 1 + 7 + 8 + 8 + 2 - 7)^{23}$
$:= (-9 + 35 - 1 + 91 + 444 - 8 + 1)^4$	$:= (9 - 4 + 14 + 3 - 1 - 7 - 8 - 8 - 2 + 7)^{23}$
$:= (9 - 35 - 1 + 91 + 4 + 4 + 481)^4$	$:= (-9 + 4 + 14 - 3 + 1 + 7 - 8 - 8 - 2 + 7)^{23}$
$:= (9 + 35 + 1 + 9 + 14 + 4 + 481)^4$	$:= (-9 + 4 + 14 - 3 - 1 - 7 + 8 - 8 - 2 + 7)^{23}$
$:= (-9 + 3 + 519 - 1 - 44 + 4 + 81)^4$	$:= (-9 - 4 + 14 + 3 + 1 - 7 + 8 - 8 - 2 + 7)^{23}$
$:= (-9 + 3 + 519 - 1 + 4 - 44 + 81)^4$	$:= (-9 + 4 + 14 - 3 - 1 - 7 - 8 + 8 - 2 + 7)^{23}$
$:= (9 + 3 + 51 - 9 + 14 + 4 + 481)^4$	$:= (-9 - 4 + 14 + 3 + 1 - 7 - 8 + 8 - 2 + 7)^{23}$
$:= (-9 + 3 + 51 + 9 + 14 + 4 + 481)^4$	$:= (9 - 4 - 14 - 3 + 1 - 7 + 8 + 8 - 2 + 7)^{23}$
$:= (93 + 519 - 14 + 4 - 48 - 1)^4$	$:= (-9 - 4 - 14 + 3 - 1 + 7 + 8 + 8 - 2 + 7)^{23}$
$:= (93 + 519 + 14 + 4 + 4 - 81)^4$	$:= (9 - 4 + 14 - 3 + 1 - 7 - 8 - 8 + 2 + 7)^{23}$
$:= (93 + 5 + 19 - 1 - 44 + 481)^4$	$:= (-9 - 4 + 14 + 3 - 1 + 7 - 8 - 8 + 2 + 7)^{23}$
$:= (93 + 5 + 1 + 91 + 444 - 81)^4$	$:= (9 + 4 - 14 + 3 + 1 + 7 - 8 - 8 + 2 + 7)^{23}$
$:= (-9 + 35 - 1 + 91 - 44 + 481)^4$	$:= (9 + 4 - 14 + 3 - 1 - 7 + 8 - 8 + 2 + 7)^{23}$
$:= (-9 - 3 - 51 + 91 + 444 + 81)^4$	$:= (9 - 4 - 14 - 3 - 1 + 7 + 8 - 8 + 2 + 7)^{23}$
$:= (-9 - 3 - 51 + 91 + 44 + 481)^4$	$:= (9 + 4 - 14 + 3 - 1 - 7 - 8 + 8 + 2 + 7)^{23}$
$:= (-9 - 3 - 51 - 9 + 144 + 481)^4$	$:= (9 - 4 - 14 - 3 - 1 + 7 - 8 + 8 + 2 + 7)^{23}$
$:= (-9 + 3 + 5 + 191 + 444 - 81)^4$	$:= (-9 + 4 - 14 + 3 + 1 - 7 + 8 + 8 + 2 + 7)^{23}$
$:= (93 + 519 - 144 + 4 + 81)^4$	$:= (-9 - 4 - 14 - 3 + 1 + 7 + 8 + 8 + 2 + 7)^{23}$
93824221184 := (938 + 2422 + 1184) ³	$:= (-9 + 4 - 1 - 4 + 31 + 7 - 8 - 8 - 2 - 7)^{23}$
93886178625 := (9 + 3886 + 17 + 8 + 625) ³	$:= (-9 - 4 - 1 + 4 + 31 + 7 - 8 - 8 - 2 - 7)^{23}$
94010175323 := (-9 + 4010 + 17 + 532 - 3) ³	$:= (9 - 4 - 1 - 4 + 31 - 7 - 8 - 8 + 2 - 7)^{23}$
94072214592 := (-9 + 40 - 72 - 2 - 1 + 4592) ³	$:= (-9 + 4 + 1 + 4 + 31 - 7 - 8 - 8 + 2 - 7)^{23}$
94072214592 := (9 + 40 - 72 - 21 + 4592) ³	$:= (-9 - 4 + 1 - 4 + 31 - 7 + 8 - 8 + 2 - 7)^{23}$
94143178827 := (9 - 4 + 14 + 3 - 1 + 7 - 8 - 8 - 2 - 7) ²³	$:= (-9 - 4 + 1 - 4 + 31 - 7 - 8 + 8 + 2 - 7)^{23}$
$:= (-9 + 4 + 14 - 3 - 1 + 7 + 8 - 8 - 2 - 7)^{23}$	$:= (9 + 4 - 1 + 4 - 31 + 7 + 8 + 8 + 2 - 7)^{23}$
$:= (-9 - 4 + 14 + 3 + 1 + 7 + 8 - 8 - 2 - 7)^{23}$	$:= (-9 + 4 - 1 - 4 + 31 - 7 - 8 - 8 - 2 + 7)^{23}$
$:= (-9 + 4 + 14 - 3 - 1 + 7 - 8 + 8 - 2 - 7)^{23}$	$:= (-9 - 4 - 1 + 4 + 31 - 7 - 8 - 8 - 2 + 7)^{23}$
$:= (-9 - 4 + 14 + 3 + 1 + 7 - 8 + 8 - 2 - 7)^{23}$	$:= (9 + 4 + 1 + 4 - 31 + 7 + 8 - 8 + 2 + 7)^{23}$
$:= (-9 - 4 + 14 + 3 - 1 - 7 + 8 + 8 - 2 - 7)^{23}$	$:= (9 + 4 + 1 + 4 - 31 + 7 - 8 + 8 + 2 + 7)^{23}$
$:= (9 + 4 - 14 + 3 + 1 - 7 + 8 + 8 - 2 - 7)^{23}$	$:= (9 + 4 - 1 + 4 - 31 - 7 + 8 + 8 + 2 + 7)^{23}$
$:= (9 - 4 - 14 - 3 + 1 + 7 + 8 + 8 - 2 - 7)^{23}$	$:= (9 - 4 + 1 - 4 - 31 + 7 + 8 + 8 + 2 + 7)^{23}$

$$\begin{aligned} &:= (9+4-1-4+3+17-8-8-2-7)^{23} &:= (94+1-4+3-1-7-88-2+7)^{23} \\ &:= (9-4-1+4+3+17-8-8-2-7)^{23} &:= (94-1-4+3+1-7-88-2+7)^{23} \\ &:= (-9+4-1+4-3+17+8-8-2-7)^{23} &:= (-94-1-4+3-1+7+88-2+7)^{23} \\ &:= (-9+4+1-4+3+17+8-8-2-7)^{23} &:= (94+1-4-3+1-7-88+2+7)^{23} \\ &:= (-9-4+1+4+3+17+8-8-2-7)^{23} &:= (-94+1+4+3-1-7+88+2+7)^{23} \\ &:= (-9+4-1+4-3+17-8+8-2-7)^{23} &:= (-94-1+4+3+1-7+88+2+7)^{23} \\ &:= (-9+4+1-4+3+17-8+8-2-7)^{23} &:= (-94+1-4-3-1+7+88+2+7)^{23} \\ &:= (-9-4+1+4+3+17-8+8-2-7)^{23} &:= (-94-1-4-3+1+7+88+2+7)^{23} \\ &:= (9+4-1+4-3-17+8+8-2-7)^{23} &:= (94-1+4-3-1+7-8-82-7)^{23} \\ &:= (9+4+1-4+3-17+8+8-2-7)^{23} &:= (94+1-4+3-1+7-8-82-7)^{23} \\ &:= (9-4+1+4+3-17+8+8-2-7)^{23} &:= (94-1-4+3+1+7-8-82-7)^{23} \\ &:= (-9-4-1-4-3+17+8+8-2-7)^{23} &:= (94-1-4+3-1-7+8-82-7)^{23} \\ &:= (9+4+1-4-3+17-8-8+2-7)^{23} &:= (-94+1+4+3-1+7+8+82-7)^{23} \\ &:= (9-4+1+4-3+17-8-8+2-7)^{23} &:= (-94-1+4+3+1+7+8+82-7)^{23} \\ &:= (9-4-1-4-3+17-8-8-2+7)^{23} &:= (94-1+4-3-1-7-8-82+7)^{23} \\ &:= (-9+4+1+4-3+17-8-8-2+7)^{23} &:= (94+1-4+3-1-7-8-82+7)^{23} \\ &:= (9+4+1+4-3-17+8-8-2+7)^{23} &:= (94-1-4+3+1-7-8-82+7)^{23} \\ &:= (-9-4+1-4-3+17+8-8-2+7)^{23} &:= (-94+1+4+3+1+7-8+82+7)^{23} \\ &:= (9+4+1+4-3-17-8+8-2+7)^{23} &:= (-94+1+4+3-1-7+8+82+7)^{23} \\ &:= (-9-4+1-4-3+17-8+8-2+7)^{23} &:= (-94-1+4+3+1-7+8+82+7)^{23} \\ &:= (9-4+1-4-3-17+8+8-2+7)^{23} &:= (-94+1-4-3-1+7+8+82+7)^{23} \\ &:= (-9+4-1-4+3+17-8-8+2+7)^{23} &:= (-94-1-4-3+1+7+8+82+7)^{23} \\ &:= (-9-4-1+4+3+17-8-8+2+7)^{23} &:= (-9+41+4-31+7+8-8-2-7)^{23} \\ &:= (9+4-1-4+3-17+8-8+2+7)^{23} &:= (-9+41+4-31+7-8+8-2-7)^{23} \\ &:= (9-4-1+4+3-17+8-8+2+7)^{23} &:= (9-41+4+31-7+8+8-2-7)^{23} \\ &:= (9+4-1-4+3-17-8+8+2+7)^{23} &:= (9+41-4-31-7+8-8+2-7)^{23} \\ &:= (9-4-1+4+3-17-8+8+2+7)^{23} &:= (9+41-4-31-7-8+8+2-7)^{23} \\ &:= (-9+4-1+4-3-17+8+8+2+7)^{23} &:= (-9-41+4+31+7+8+8+2-7)^{23} \\ &:= (-9+4+1-4+3-17+8+8+2+7)^{23} &:= (-9+41+4-31-7+8-8-2+7)^{23} \\ &:= (-9-4+1+4+3-17+8+8+2+7)^{23} &:= (-9+41+4-31-7-8+8-2+7)^{23} \\ &:= (94-1+4-3-1+7-88-2-7)^{23} &:= (9-41+4+31+7-8-8+2+7)^{23} \\ &:= (94+1-4+3-1+7-88-2-7)^{23} &:= (-9-41+4+31-7+8+8+2+7)^{23} \\ &:= (94-1-4+3+1+7-88-2-7)^{23} &:= (-9+41-4-3-17+8-8+2-7)^{23} \\ &:= (94+1+4+3+1-7-88+2-7)^{23} &:= (-9+41-4-3-17-8+8+2-7)^{23} \\ &:= (94+1-4-3+1+7-88+2-7)^{23} &:= (9-41+4+3+17+8+8+2-7)^{23} \\ &:= (-94+1+4+3-1+7+88+2-7)^{23} &:= (-9+41-4+3-17-8-8-2+7)^{23} \\ &:= (-94-1+4+3+1+7+88+2-7)^{23} &:= (9-41-4-3+17+8+8+2+7)^{23} \\ &:= (94-1+4-3-1-7-88-2+7)^{23} &:= (-9-41-4-3-1+78-8-2-7)^{23} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} &:= (9+4+14-3-1+7+8-8-27)^{23} & &:= (9-4-1-4-3+17+8+8-27)^{23} \\ &:= (9-4+14+3+1+7+8-8-27)^{23} & &:= (-9+4+1+4-3+17+8+8-27)^{23} \\ &:= (9+4+14-3-1+7-8+8-27)^{23} & &:= (-9+4-1-4+3-17+8-8+27)^{23} \\ &:= (9-4+14+3+1+7-8+8-27)^{23} & &:= (-9-4-1+4+3-17+8-8+27)^{23} \\ &:= (9-4+14+3-1-7+8+8-27)^{23} & &:= (-9+4-1-4+3-17-8+8+27)^{23} \\ &:= (-9+4+14-3+1+7+8+8-27)^{23} & &:= (-9-4-1+4+3-17-8+8+27)^{23} \\ &:= (-9-4+14-3+1-7-8-8+27)^{23} & &:= (9+4+1+4-3-1+78-82-7)^{23} \\ &:= (-9+4-14+3+1+7-8-8+27)^{23} & &:= (9+4-1+4-3+1+78-82-7)^{23} \\ &:= (-9+4-14+3-1-7+8-8+27)^{23} & &:= (9+4+1-4+3+1+78-82-7)^{23} \\ &:= (-9-4-14-3-1+7+8-8+27)^{23} & &:= (9-4+1+4+3+1+78-82-7)^{23} \\ &:= (-9+4-14+3-1-7-8+8+27)^{23} & &:= (9+4+1-4-3-1-78+82-7)^{23} \\ &:= (-9-4-14-3-1+7-8+8+27)^{23} & &:= (9-4+1+4-3-1-78+82-7)^{23} \\ &:= (-9-4-1+43-17+8-8-2-7)^{23} & &:= (9+4-1-4-3+1-78+82-7)^{23} \\ &:= (-9-4-1+43-17-8+8-2-7)^{23} & &:= (9-4-1+4-3+1-78+82-7)^{23} \\ &:= (-9-4+1+43-17-8-8-2+7)^{23} & &:= (9-4+1-4+3+1-78+82-7)^{23} \\ &:= (9-4-1-43+17+8+8+2+7)^{23} & &:= (-9+4-1+4+3-1+78-82+7)^{23} \\ &:= (-9-4-1-43-1+78-8-2-7)^{23} & &:= (9-4+1-4-3+1+78-82+7)^{23} \\ &:= (9+4-1-4+31+7-8-8-27)^{23} & &:= (-9+4-1-4+3-1-78+82+7)^{23} \\ &:= (9-4-1+4+31+7-8-8-27)^{23} & &:= (-9-4-1+4+3-1-78+82+7)^{23} \\ &:= (-9+4+1-4+31+7+8-8-27)^{23} & &:= (94-14+3-1-78+8-2-7)^{23} \\ &:= (-9-4+1+4+31+7+8-8-27)^{23} & &:= (94-14-3+1-78+8+2-7)^{23} \\ &:= (-9+4+1-4+31+7-8+8-27)^{23} & &:= (-94+14+3-1+78+8+2-7)^{23} \\ &:= (-9-4+1+4+31+7-8+8-27)^{23} & &:= (94-14+3+1-78-8-2+7)^{23} \\ &:= (-9+4-1-4+31-7+8+8-27)^{23} & &:= (-94+14+3+1+78-8+2+7)^{23} \\ &:= (-9-4-1+4+31-7+8+8-27)^{23} & &:= (94+1-43+1-7-8-8-27)^{23} \\ &:= (9+4-1+4-31+7-8-8+27)^{23} & &:= (-94+1+4+31+78-8-2-7)^{23} \\ &:= (9-4-1-4-31+7+8-8+27)^{23} & &:= (94+1+4-31-78+8-2+7)^{23} \\ &:= (-9+4+1+4-31+7+8-8+27)^{23} & &:= (9-41+43+17-8-8-2-7)^{23} \\ &:= (9-4-1-4-31+7-8+8+27)^{23} & &:= (9+41-43+17-8-8+2-7)^{23} \\ &:= (-9+4+1+4-31+7-8+8+27)^{23} & &:= (-9-41+43+17-8-8+2+7)^{23} \\ &:= (-9+4-1+4-31-7+8+8+27)^{23} & &:= (9-41+43-17+8-8+2+7)^{23} \\ &:= (-9-4+1-4-31+7+8+8+27)^{23} & &:= (9-41+43-17-8+8+2+7)^{23} \\ &:= (9+4-1+4-3+17+8-8-27)^{23} & &:= (9-41-43+1+78+8-2-7)^{23} \\ &:= (9+4+1-4+3+17+8-8-27)^{23} & &:= (9+41+43+1-78-8+2-7)^{23} \\ &:= (9-4+1+4+3+17+8-8-27)^{23} & &:= (9-41-43-1+78-8+2+7)^{23} \\ &:= (9+4-1+4-3+17-8+8-27)^{23} & &:= (-9-41-43+1+78+8+2+7)^{23} \\ &:= (9+4+1-4+3+17-8+8-27)^{23} & &:= (9+41-4+31+7+8-82-7)^{23} \\ &:= (9-4+1+4+3+17-8+8-27)^{23} & &:= (9+41-4+31-7+8-82+7)^{23} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} &:= (-9 - 41 - 4 - 31 + 7 - 8 + 82 + 7)^{23} \\ &:= (9 + 41 + 4 - 31 + 7 + 8 - 8 - 27)^{23} \\ &:= (9 + 41 + 4 - 31 + 7 - 8 + 8 - 27)^{23} \\ &:= (-9 - 41 + 4 + 31 + 7 - 8 - 8 + 27)^{23} \\ &:= (-9 + 41 - 4 + 3 - 17 + 8 + 8 - 27)^{23} \\ &:= (9 - 41 + 4 + 3 + 17 - 8 - 8 + 27)^{23} \\ &:= (-9 - 41 - 4 - 3 + 17 + 8 + 8 + 27)^{23} \\ &:= (9 - 41 - 4 - 3 - 1 + 78 - 8 - 27)^{23} \\ &:= (-9 - 41 - 4 - 3 + 1 + 78 + 8 - 27)^{23} \\ &:= (-9 - 4 - 14 - 31 + 78 - 8 - 2 - 7)^{23} \\ &:= (-9 + 4 + 1 - 43 - 17 - 8 + 82 - 7)^{23} \\ &:= (-9 - 4 - 1 + 43 + 17 - 8 - 8 - 27)^{23} \\ &:= (9 - 4 - 1 + 43 - 17 + 8 - 8 - 27)^{23} \\ &:= (9 - 4 - 1 + 43 - 17 - 8 + 8 - 27)^{23} \\ &:= (-9 - 4 + 1 + 43 - 17 + 8 + 8 - 27)^{23} \\ &:= (-9 - 4 - 1 - 43 + 17 + 8 + 8 + 27)^{23} \\ &:= (9 - 4 - 1 - 43 - 1 + 78 - 8 - 27)^{23} \\ &:= (-9 - 4 + 1 - 43 - 1 + 78 + 8 - 27)^{23} \\ &:= (-9 - 4 - 1 - 43 + 1 + 78 + 8 - 27)^{23} \\ &:= (9 - 4 - 1 + 43 - 1 - 78 + 8 + 27)^{23} \\ &:= (94 + 14 - 31 + 7 + 8 - 82 - 7)^{23} \\ &:= (94 + 14 - 31 - 7 + 8 - 82 + 7)^{23} \\ &:= (94 - 14 + 3 + 17 - 88 - 2 - 7)^{23} \\ &:= (-94 + 14 + 3 - 17 + 88 + 2 + 7)^{23} \\ &:= (-94 - 14 - 3 + 17 + 88 + 2 + 7)^{23} \\ &:= (94 - 14 + 3 + 17 - 8 - 82 - 7)^{23} \\ &:= (-94 + 14 + 3 - 17 + 8 + 82 + 7)^{23} \\ &:= (-94 - 14 - 3 + 17 + 8 + 82 + 7)^{23} \\ &:= (-94 - 14 - 3 + 1 + 78 + 8 + 27)^{23} \\ &:= (-94 + 1 + 43 - 1 - 7 + 88 - 27)^{23} \\ &:= (-94 - 1 + 43 + 1 - 7 + 88 - 27)^{23} \\ &:= (-94 + 1 + 4 + 3 + 178 - 82 - 7)^{23} \\ &:= (-94 + 1 - 4 - 3 + 178 - 82 + 7)^{23} \\ &:= (94 - 1 - 4 + 3 - 178 + 82 + 7)^{23} \\ &:= (-9 - 41 - 43 + 17 + 88 - 2 - 7)^{23} \\ &:= (-9 - 41 + 43 - 17 + 8 - 8 + 27)^{23} \\ &:= (-9 - 41 + 43 - 17 - 8 + 8 + 27)^{23} \\ &:= (9 + 41 - 43 - 1 - 78 + 82 - 7)^{23} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} &:= (-9 - 41 + 43 - 1 - 78 + 82 + 7)^{23} \\ &:= (-9 - 41 - 43 - 1 + 78 - 8 + 27)^{23} \\ &:= (9 - 4 - 14 - 31 + 78 - 8 - 27)^{23} \\ &:= (9 - 4 - 1 + 43 + 17 - 88 + 27)^{23} \\ &:= (941 - 43 + 1 - 7 - 882 - 7)^{23} \\ &:= (94 - 14 + 31 + 7 - 88 - 27)^{23} \\ &:= (9 - 41 - 43 + 17 + 88 - 27)^{23} \\ &:= (-9 - 4 - 143 + 178 + 8 - 27)^{23} \\ &94197431056 := (9 + 419 + 74 - 3 - 1 + 056)^4 \\ &:= (94 + 1 + 97 - 4 + 310 + 56)^4 \\ &:= (-9 + 4 + 197 - 4 + 310 + 56)^4 \\ &:= (-9 - 4 + 197 + 4 + 310 + 56)^4 \\ &94320644608 := (-9 - 43 - 2 - 06 + 4 + 4608)^3 \\ &94320644608 := (9 + 4 - 3 - 2 - 064 + 4608)^3 \\ &94320644608 := (9 - 43 - 20 - 6 + 4 + 4608)^3 \\ &94382820377 := (9 + 4382 + 82 + 03 + 77)^3 \\ &94445023464 := (9 + 44 + 4502 - 3 + 4 - 6 + 4)^3 \\ &:= (-9 + 44 + 4502 + 3 + 4 + 6 + 4)^3 \\ &:= (-9 + 4 + 4 + 4502 + 3 + 46 + 4)^3 \\ &:= (9 + 4445 + 02 + 34 + 64)^3 \\ &:= (9 + 4 + 4450 + 23 + 4 + 64)^3 \\ &:= (-9 + 4 + 4 - 4 + 5023 - 464)^3 \\ &:= (-9 + 4 - 4 + 4 + 5023 - 464)^3 \\ &:= (-9 - 4 + 4 + 4 + 5023 - 464)^3 \\ &94507253875 := (-9 + 4507 - 2 + 53 + 8 - 7 + 5)^3 \\ &:= (9 + 4507 - 2 + 5 + 38 - 7 + 5)^3 \\ &:= (-9 + 4507 + 2 + 5 + 38 + 7 + 5)^3 \\ &:= (-9 + 4507 - 2 - 5 - 3 - 8 + 75)^3 \\ &:= (9 + 4507 - 25 - 3 - 8 + 75)^3 \\ &:= (9 - 4 - 50 + 725 + 3875)^3 \\ &94569511616 := (-9 + 4569 - 5 + 1 + 1 + 6 - 1 - 6)^3 \\ &:= (-9 + 4569 + 5 + 1 + 1 - 6 + 1 - 6)^3 \\ &:= (-9 + 4569 - 5 + 1 - 1 + 6 + 1 - 6)^3 \\ &:= (-9 + 4569 - 5 - 1 + 1 + 6 + 1 - 6)^3 \\ &:= (-9 + 4569 - 5 + 1 + 1 - 6 - 1 + 6)^3 \\ &:= (-9 + 4569 - 5 + 1 - 1 - 6 + 1 + 6)^3 \\ &:= (-9 + 4569 - 5 - 1 + 1 - 6 + 1 + 6)^3 \\ &:= (-9 + 4569 - 5 + 11 + 6 - 16)^3 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} & := (-9 + 4569 - 5 + 1 + 16 - 16)^3 & := (-9 + 49 - 3 + 1 + 8 - 7 - 7 - 1 + 3 + 3)^7 \\ & := (-9 + 4569 - 5 + 1 - 16 + 16)^3 & := (-9 + 49 - 3 - 1 + 8 - 7 - 7 + 1 + 3 + 3)^7 \\ \mathbf{94631796693} & := (9 + 4631 + 7 - 96 - 6 + 9 + 3)^3 & := (-9 + 49 - 3 + 1 - 8 + 7 - 7 + 1 + 3 + 3)^7 \\ & := (9 + 4631 + 7 - 9 + 6 + 6 - 93)^3 & := (-9 + 49 - 3 + 1 - 8 - 7 + 7 + 1 + 3 + 3)^7 \\ & := (-9 + 4631 + 7 + 9 + 6 + 6 - 93)^3 & := (94 - 9 - 31 - 8 - 7 - 7 - 1 + 3 + 3)^7 \\ \mathbf{94694109112} & := (-9 + 469 + 4109 + 1 - 12)^3 & := (94 + 9 + 3 + 1 + 8 - 77 - 1 + 3 - 3)^7 \\ \mathbf{94756448879} & := (9 + 47 + 5 - 6 + 4488 + 7 + 9)^3 & := (94 + 9 + 3 - 1 + 8 - 77 + 1 + 3 - 3)^7 \\ \mathbf{94879400625} & := (9 - 4 + 8 - 79 - 4 + 00625)^4 & := (94 + 9 + 3 + 1 + 8 - 77 - 1 - 3 + 3)^7 \\ & := (9 + 4 - 8 - 79 + 4 + 00625)^4 & := (94 + 9 + 3 - 1 + 8 - 77 + 1 - 3 + 3)^7 \\ & := (948 + 7 + 9 - 400 - 6 + 2 - 5)^4 & := (94 + 9 - 3 + 1 + 8 - 77 - 1 + 3 + 3)^7 \\ & := (948 + 7 - 9 - 400 + 6 - 2 + 5)^4 & := (94 + 9 - 3 - 1 + 8 - 77 + 1 + 3 + 3)^7 \\ & := (94 - 8 - 7 + 9 + 400 + 62 + 5)^4 & := (94 + 9 - 3 - 1 + 8 + 7 - 71 - 3 - 3)^7 \\ & := (9 + 48 + 79 + 400 - 6 + 25)^4 & := (94 + 9 + 3 + 1 + 8 - 7 - 71 + 3 - 3)^7 \\ \mathbf{94931877133} & := (9 + 4 + 9 - 3 + 1 + 8 + 7 + 7 + 1 - 3 - 3)^7 & := (94 + 9 + 3 + 1 + 8 - 7 - 71 - 3 + 3)^7 \\ & := (9 - 4 + 9 + 3 - 1 + 8 + 7 + 7 - 1 + 3 - 3)^7 & := (94 + 9 - 3 + 1 + 8 - 7 - 71 + 3 + 3)^7 \\ & := (9 - 4 + 9 + 3 - 1 + 8 + 7 + 7 - 1 - 3 + 3)^7 & := (94 - 9 + 3 - 1 + 8 + 7 - 71 + 3 + 3)^7 \\ & := (9 + 4 + 9 + 3 - 1 + 8 + 7 - 7 - 1 + 3 + 3)^7 & := (9 - 49 + 3 + 1 + 87 - 7 - 1 - 3 - 3)^7 \\ & := (9 + 4 + 9 + 3 - 1 + 8 - 7 + 7 - 1 + 3 + 3)^7 & := (9 - 49 + 3 - 1 + 87 - 7 + 1 - 3 - 3)^7 \\ & := (9 + 4 + 9 + 3 + 1 - 8 + 7 + 7 - 1 + 3 + 3)^7 & := (9 - 49 - 3 + 1 + 87 - 7 - 1 + 3 - 3)^7 \\ & := (9 - 4 + 9 - 3 - 1 + 8 + 7 + 7 - 1 + 3 + 3)^7 & := (-9 - 49 + 3 - 1 + 87 + 7 - 1 + 3 - 3)^7 \\ & := (9 + 4 + 9 + 3 - 1 - 8 + 7 + 7 + 1 + 3 + 3)^7 & := (9 - 49 - 3 - 1 + 87 - 7 + 1 + 3 - 3)^7 \\ & := (9 + 4 - 9 + 3 + 1 + 8 + 7 + 7 + 1 + 3 + 3)^7 & := (9 - 49 - 3 + 1 + 87 - 7 - 1 - 3 + 3)^7 \\ & := (-9 + 4 + 9 + 3 + 1 + 8 + 7 + 7 + 1 + 3 + 3)^7 & := (-9 - 49 + 3 - 1 + 87 + 7 - 1 - 3 + 3)^7 \\ & := (-9 + 49 - 3 - 1 + 8 + 7 - 7 - 1 - 3 - 3)^7 & := (9 - 49 - 3 - 1 + 87 - 7 + 1 - 3 + 3)^7 \\ & := (-9 + 49 - 3 - 1 + 8 - 7 + 7 - 1 - 3 - 3)^7 & := (-9 - 49 - 3 - 1 + 87 + 7 - 1 + 3 + 3)^7 \\ & := (-9 + 49 - 3 + 1 - 8 + 7 + 7 - 1 - 3 - 3)^7 & := (9 + 4 + 93 + 1 + 8 - 77 - 1 + 3 - 3)^7 \\ & := (-9 + 49 - 3 - 1 - 8 + 7 + 7 + 1 - 3 - 3)^7 & := (9 + 4 + 93 - 1 + 8 - 77 + 1 + 3 - 3)^7 \\ & := (9 + 49 + 3 - 1 - 8 - 7 - 7 - 1 + 3 - 3)^7 & := (9 + 4 + 93 + 1 + 8 - 77 - 1 - 3 + 3)^7 \\ & := (-9 + 49 + 3 + 1 + 8 - 7 - 7 - 1 + 3 - 3)^7 & := (9 + 4 + 93 - 1 + 8 - 77 + 1 - 3 + 3)^7 \\ & := (-9 + 49 + 3 - 1 + 8 - 7 - 7 + 1 + 3 - 3)^7 & := (9 - 4 + 93 + 1 + 8 - 77 + 1 + 3 + 3)^7 \\ & := (-9 + 49 + 3 + 1 - 8 + 7 - 7 + 1 + 3 - 3)^7 & := (9 - 4 + 93 + 1 + 8 + 7 - 71 - 3 - 3)^7 \\ & := (-9 + 49 + 3 + 1 - 8 - 7 + 7 + 1 + 3 - 3)^7 & := (9 + 4 + 93 + 1 + 8 - 7 - 71 + 3 - 3)^7 \\ & := (9 + 49 + 3 - 1 - 8 - 7 - 7 - 1 - 3 + 3)^7 & := (9 + 4 + 93 + 1 + 8 - 7 - 71 - 3 + 3)^7 \\ & := (-9 + 49 + 3 + 1 + 8 - 7 - 7 - 1 - 3 + 3)^7 & := (-9 + 4 + 93 - 1 + 8 + 7 - 71 + 3 + 3)^7 \\ & := (-9 + 49 + 3 - 1 + 8 - 7 - 7 + 1 - 3 + 3)^7 & := (-9 - 4 + 93 - 1 - 8 + 7 - 7 - 1 - 33)^7 \\ & := (-9 + 49 + 3 + 1 - 8 + 7 - 7 + 1 - 3 + 3)^7 & := (-9 - 4 + 93 - 1 - 8 - 7 + 7 - 1 - 33)^7 \\ & := (-9 + 49 + 3 + 1 - 8 - 7 + 7 + 1 - 3 + 3)^7 & := (9 + 4 - 9 - 31 - 8 + 77 + 1 - 3 - 3)^7 \\ & := (9 + 49 - 3 - 1 - 8 - 7 - 7 - 1 + 3 + 3)^7 & := (-9 + 4 + 9 - 31 - 8 + 77 + 1 - 3 - 3)^7 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} & := (-9-4-9-31+8+77-1+3+3)^7 & := (-9+4-9-3+1+8+77+1-33)^7 \\ & := (9+4-9-31-8+7+71-3-3)^7 & := (9-4-9+3-1+8-7+71-33)^7 \\ & := (-9+4+9-31-8+7+71-3-3)^7 & := (-9-4+9+3-1+8-7+71-33)^7 \\ & := (9-4-9-31+8-7+71+3-3)^7 & := (9+4-9-3-1-8+7+71-33)^7 \\ & := (-9-4+9-31+8-7+71+3-3)^7 & := (-9+4+9-3-1-8+7+71-33)^7 \\ & := (9-4-9-31+8-7+71-3+3)^7 & := (9-4-9+3+1-8+7+71-33)^7 \\ & := (-9-4+9-31+8-7+71-3+3)^7 & := (-9-4+9+3+1-8+7+71-33)^7 \\ & := (9-4+9+31+8+7-7-13-3)^7 & := (-9+4-9-3+1+8+7+71-33)^7 \\ & := (9-4+9+31+8-7+7-13-3)^7 & := (94-9+31-87+7+1+3-3)^7 \\ & := (9+4-9+31-8+7-7+13-3)^7 & := (94-9+31-87+7+1-3+3)^7 \\ & := (-9+4+9+31-8+7-7+13-3)^7 & := (94+9+3+1-87+7+13-3)^7 \\ & := (9+4-9+31-8-7+7+13-3)^7 & := (94+9-3+1-87+7+13+3)^7 \\ & := (-9+4+9+31-8-7+7+13-3)^7 & := (94+9-3-1-87-7-1+33)^7 \\ & := (9+4+9+31+8-7-7-13+3)^7 & := (-94+9-3-1+87+7-1+33)^7 \\ & := (9-4-9+31+8-7-7+13+3)^7 & := (94-9-3+1-87+7+1+33)^7 \\ & := (-9-4+9+31+8-7-7+13+3)^7 & := (-9-49+31-8+77+1-3-3)^7 \\ & := (9-4-9+31-8-7-7-1+33)^7 & := (-9-49+31-8+7+71-3-3)^7 \\ & := (-9-4+9+31-8-7-7-1+33)^7 & := (9+49-31+8-7-7+13+3)^7 \\ & := (9-4+9-31+8+7+7-1+33)^7 & := (9+49-31-8-7-7-1+33)^7 \\ & := (-9-4-9+31+8-7-7+1+33)^7 & := (-9+49-31+8-7-7+1+33)^7 \\ & := (-9+4-9-3-18+77+1-3-3)^7 & := (-9+49+3+18-7-7-13+3)^7 \\ & := (-9+4-9-3-18+7+71-3-3)^7 & := (-9+49-3+18+7+7+1-33)^7 \\ & := (9-4+9+3+18-7-7+13+3)^7 & := (-9+49-3-18-7-7-1+33)^7 \\ & := (9+4+9+3-18+7+7+13+3)^7 & := (9-49-3+1-8+77+13-3)^7 \\ & := (-9+4-9+3+18+7+7+13+3)^7 & := (9-49+3-1+8+77-13+3)^7 \\ & := (9+4-9-3+18-7-7-1+33)^7 & := (9+49+3-1+8+7-71+33)^7 \\ & := (-9+4+9-3+18-7-7-1+33)^7 & := (9+4+93+1-87+7+13-3)^7 \\ & := (9-4-9+3+18-7-7+1+33)^7 & := (9-4+93+1-87-7-1+33)^7 \\ & := (-9-4+9+3+18-7-7+1+33)^7 & := (9-4-93-1+87+7-1+33)^7 \\ & := (9+4-9+3-18+7+7+1+33)^7 & := (9-4+93-1-87-7+1+33)^7 \\ & := (-9+4+9+3-18+7+7+1+33)^7 & := (9-4-9+31+87-71-3-3)^7 \\ & := (-9+4-9-3+1-8+77-13-3)^7 & := (-9-4+9+31+87-71-3-3)^7 \\ & := (9+4-9-3+1-8+77-1-33)^7 & := (9+4+9+31-87+71+3-3)^7 \\ & := (-9+4+9-3+1-8+77-1-33)^7 & := (9+4+9+31-87+71-3+3)^7 \\ & := (9+4-9-3-1-8+77+1-33)^7 & := (9+4-9-31+87-7-13-3)^7 \\ & := (-9+4+9-3-1-8+77+1-33)^7 & := (-9+4+9-31+87-7-13-3)^7 \\ & := (9-4-9+3+1-8+77+1-33)^7 & := (-9-4-9-31+87-7+13-3)^7 \\ & := (-9-4+9+3+1-8+77+1-33)^7 & := (9+4+9-31+87-7-1-33)^7 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} &:= (-9 + 4 - 9 + 3 - 1 + 87 - 71 + 33)^7 \\ &:= (9 + 4 + 9 - 3 + 1 - 87 + 71 + 33)^7 \\ &:= (9 - 4 - 9 + 3 - 1 - 87 - 7 + 133)^7 \\ &:= (-9 - 4 + 9 + 3 - 1 - 87 - 7 + 133)^7 \\ &:= (-9 + 4 - 9 - 3 + 1 - 87 + 7 + 133)^7 \\ &:= (94 - 93 + 18 - 7 - 7 - 1 + 33)^7 \\ &:= (-94 + 93 + 18 - 7 - 7 + 1 + 33)^7 \\ &:= (94 - 93 + 1 - 8 + 77 - 1 - 33)^7 \\ &:= (94 - 93 - 1 - 8 + 77 + 1 - 33)^7 \\ &:= (-94 + 93 + 1 - 8 + 77 + 1 - 33)^7 \\ &:= (-94 + 93 - 1 + 8 - 7 + 71 - 33)^7 \\ &:= (94 - 93 - 1 - 8 + 7 + 71 - 33)^7 \\ &:= (-94 + 93 + 1 - 8 + 7 + 71 - 33)^7 \\ &:= (94 - 9 + 31 + 8 - 77 - 13 + 3)^7 \\ &:= (94 + 9 - 31 + 8 - 77 + 1 + 33)^7 \\ &:= (94 + 9 + 3 + 18 - 77 - 13 + 3)^7 \\ &:= (94 + 9 - 3 - 18 - 77 - 1 + 33)^7 \\ &:= (94 + 9 - 3 - 18 - 7 - 71 + 33)^7 \\ &:= (-94 - 9 + 3 + 18 - 7 - 7 + 133)^7 \\ &:= (94 + 9 - 3 + 1 - 8 + 77 - 133)^7 \\ &:= (9 + 49 - 31 + 87 - 71 - 3 - 3)^7 \\ &:= (-9 - 49 + 31 + 87 - 7 - 13 - 3)^7 \\ &:= (9 - 49 + 31 + 87 - 7 - 1 - 33)^7 \\ &:= (-9 - 49 - 31 + 87 + 7 - 1 + 33)^7 \\ &:= (9 + 49 - 3 - 1 + 87 - 71 - 33)^7 \\ &:= (9 + 4 + 93 + 18 - 77 - 13 + 3)^7 \\ &:= (-9 - 4 + 93 + 18 - 77 + 13 + 3)^7 \\ &:= (9 - 4 + 93 - 18 - 77 + 1 + 33)^7 \\ &:= (9 + 4 - 9 - 31 + 8 - 77 + 133)^7 \\ &:= (-9 + 4 + 9 - 31 + 8 - 77 + 133)^7 \\ &:= (9 - 4 - 9 + 3 - 18 - 77 + 133)^7 \\ &:= (-9 - 4 + 9 + 3 - 18 - 77 + 133)^7 \\ &:= (-94 + 93 - 1 - 87 - 7 + 133)^7 \\ &:= (94 - 9 - 31 + 87 - 71 - 33)^7 \\ &:= (-9 - 49 + 31 + 8 - 77 + 133)^7 \\ &:= (9 - 49 + 3 + 18 - 77 + 133)^7 \\ &:= (9 - 4 + 93 - 187 - 7 + 133)^7 \\ &:= (-94 + 93 - 18 - 77 + 133)^7 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{95068558144} &:= (9 + 5068 - 558 + 1 + 44)^3 \\ \mathbf{95193593496} &:= (9 + 5193 - 593 - 49 + 6)^3 \\ \mathbf{95318738432} &:= (-9 + 5318 - 738 - 4 + 3 - 2)^3 \\ \mathbf{95330885049} &:= (-95 - 3 + 308850 - 4 + 9)^2 \\ &:= (9 - 53 + 308850 - 49)^2 \\ \mathbf{95388992557} &:= (95 - 3 + 88 - 9 - 9 + 2 + 5 - 5 - 7)^5 \\ &:= (95 - 3 + 88 - 9 - 9 + 2 - 5 + 5 - 7)^5 \\ &:= (95 - 3 + 88 - 9 - 9 - 2 - 5 - 5 + 7)^5 \\ &:= (9 + 53 - 8 + 89 + 9 + 2 + 5 + 5 - 7)^5 \\ &:= (9 + 53 - 8 + 89 + 9 - 2 + 5 - 5 + 7)^5 \\ &:= (9 + 53 - 8 + 89 + 9 - 2 - 5 + 5 + 7)^5 \\ &:= (-9 - 5 + 3 + 88 + 99 - 2 - 5 - 5 - 7)^5 \\ &:= (-9 + 5 - 3 + 88 - 9 + 92 + 5 - 5 - 7)^5 \\ &:= (-9 + 5 - 3 + 88 - 9 + 92 - 5 + 5 - 7)^5 \\ &:= (-9 - 5 - 3 + 88 - 9 + 92 + 5 + 5 - 7)^5 \\ &:= (-9 - 5 + 3 + 88 - 9 + 92 - 5 - 5 + 7)^5 \\ &:= (9 - 5 - 3 + 88 + 9 + 9 + 2 + 55 - 7)^5 \\ &:= (9 - 5 - 3 + 88 + 9 + 9 - 2 - 5 + 57)^5 \\ &:= (9 - 5 - 3 - 8 + 89 + 92 - 5 - 5 - 7)^5 \\ &:= (9 + 5 + 3 - 8 + 89 + 9 + 2 + 55 - 7)^5 \\ &:= (9 - 5 - 3 + 8 + 89 + 9 + 2 + 55 - 7)^5 \\ &:= (9 - 5 + 3 - 8 + 89 + 9 - 2 + 55 + 7)^5 \\ &:= (9 + 5 + 3 - 8 + 89 + 9 - 2 - 5 + 57)^5 \\ &:= (9 - 5 - 3 + 8 + 89 + 9 - 2 - 5 + 57)^5 \\ &:= (9 - 5 + 3 - 8 + 89 + 9 - 2 + 5 + 57)^5 \\ &:= (95 - 38 - 8 + 99 + 2 + 5 - 5 + 7)^5 \\ &:= (95 - 38 - 8 + 99 + 2 - 5 + 5 + 7)^5 \\ &:= (95 - 38 - 8 + 9 + 92 + 5 - 5 + 7)^5 \\ &:= (95 - 38 - 8 + 9 + 92 - 5 + 5 + 7)^5 \\ &:= (95 + 38 - 8 - 9 - 9 + 2 + 55 - 7)^5 \\ &:= (95 + 38 - 8 - 9 - 9 - 2 - 5 + 57)^5 \\ &:= (95 - 3 + 88 + 9 - 9 - 25 - 5 + 7)^5 \\ &:= (95 - 3 + 88 - 9 + 9 - 25 - 5 + 7)^5 \\ &:= (95 - 3 + 8 + 89 - 9 - 25 - 5 + 7)^5 \\ &:= (95 + 3 - 8 + 89 - 9 - 25 + 5 + 7)^5 \\ &:= (95 - 3 + 8 + 8 + 99 - 2 - 55 + 7)^5 \\ &:= (95 - 3 + 8 + 8 + 99 + 2 + 5 - 57)^5 \\ &:= (95 - 3 + 8 + 8 + 9 + 92 + 5 - 57)^5 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 &:= (9 + 53 - 8 + 89 - 9 + 25 + 5 - 7)^5 & &:= (95 + 565 - 06 - 6 + 4 - 96)^4 \\
 &:= (-9 + 53 - 8 + 89 + 9 + 25 + 5 - 7)^5 & &:= (9 + 556 + 50 - 66 + 4 + 9 - 6)^4 \\
 &:= (-9 + 5 + 38 - 8 - 9 + 92 + 55 - 7)^5 & &:= (-9 + 556 - 50 + 66 - 4 - 9 + 6)^4 \\
 &:= (9 - 5 + 3 + 88 + 99 - 25 - 5 - 7)^5 & &:= (9 - 55 - 65 + 0664 + 9 - 6)^4 \\
 &:= (-9 + 5 - 3 + 88 + 99 - 25 - 5 + 7)^5 & &:= (9 + 5 + 565 - 066 + 49 - 6)^4 \\
 &:= (-9 - 5 - 3 + 88 + 99 - 25 + 5 + 7)^5 & &:= (9 + 55 + 650 - 66 + 4 - 96)^4 \\
 &:= (9 - 5 - 3 - 88 - 9 - 9 + 255 + 7)^5 & &**95569357248** := (955 + 6 - 9 + 3572 + 48)^3 \\
 &:= (-9 - 5 - 3 - 88 + 9 - 9 + 255 + 7)^5 & &**95946108552** := (9 - 5 + 9 + 4610 + 8 - 55 + 2)^3 \\
 &:= (-9 - 5 - 3 - 88 - 9 + 9 + 255 + 7)^5 & &:= (9 + 5 + 9 + 4610 - 8 + 5 - 52)^3 \\
 &:= (-9 + 5 + 3 + 8 - 89 - 9 + 255 - 7)^5 & &:= (-9 + 59 + 4610 - 85 + 5 - 2)^3 \\
 &:= (9 - 5 - 3 - 8 - 89 - 9 + 255 + 7)^5 & &**96103100025** := (-9 + 6 + 1 + 0310002 + 5)^2 \\
 &:= (-9 - 5 - 3 - 8 - 89 + 9 + 255 + 7)^5 & &**96197825368** := (9 + 6 - 19 - 782 + 5368)^3 \\
 &:= (95 + 38 - 8 + 9 - 9 - 25 + 57)^5 & &**96254442001** := (-9 + 625 - 44 + 4 - 20 + 01)^4 \\
 &:= (95 + 38 - 8 - 9 + 9 - 25 + 57)^5 & &:= (-9 + 625 + 4 - 44 - 20 + 01)^4 \\
 &:= (95 - 3 - 88 + 99 + 2 - 5 + 57)^5 & &:= (96 + 254 + 4 + 4 + 200 - 1)^4 \\
 &:= (95 - 3 - 88 + 9 + 92 - 5 + 57)^5 & &**96310294921** := (9 + 6 + 310294 + 9 + 21)^2 \\
 &:= (95 + 3 + 8 - 89 + 92 + 55 - 7)^5 & &**96449982056** := (96 + 4499 - 8 - 2 - 05 + 6)^3 \\
 &:= (-9 - 53 + 88 - 9 + 92 + 55 - 7)^5 & &:= (9 - 6 + 4499 + 8 + 20 + 56)^3 \\
 &:= (9 - 5 - 388 - 9 - 9 + 2 + 557)^5 & &**96639388469** := (-9 + 6 + 639 + 3884 + 69)^3 \\
 &:= (-9 - 5 - 388 + 9 - 9 + 2 + 557)^5 & &**96889010407** := (9 - 6 + 8 + 8 + 9 - 010 - 4 - 07)^{13} \\
 &:= (-9 - 5 - 388 - 9 + 9 + 2 + 557)^5 & &:= (9 + 6 - 8 - 8 + 9 + 010 - 4 - 07)^{13} \\
 &:= (-9 - 5 + 38 + 89 + 92 - 55 + 7)^5 & &:= (9 - 6 + 8 - 8 - 9 + 010 - 4 + 07)^{13} \\
 &:= (-9 + 5 + 38 - 8 + 99 - 25 + 57)^5 & &:= (9 - 6 - 8 + 8 - 9 + 010 - 4 + 07)^{13} \\
 &:= (-95 + 388 - 99 - 25 - 5 - 7)^5 & &:= (-9 - 6 + 8 - 8 + 9 + 010 - 4 + 07)^{13} \\
 &:= (-9 - 53 + 88 + 99 - 25 + 57)^5 & &:= (-9 - 6 - 8 + 8 + 9 + 010 - 4 + 07)^{13} \\
 &:= (-95 - 388 - 9 + 92 + 557)^5 & &:= (9 + 6 + 8 - 8 - 9 - 010 + 4 + 07)^{13} \\
 &**95565066496** := (9 + 5 + 565 - 06 - 6 + 4 - 9 - 6)^4 & &:= (9 + 6 - 8 + 8 - 9 - 010 + 4 + 07)^{13} \\
 &:= (9 - 5 + 565 - 06 - 6 - 4 + 9 - 6)^4 & &:= (-9 + 6 + 8 - 8 + 9 - 010 + 4 + 07)^{13} \\
 &:= (-9 + 5 + 565 - 06 - 6 + 4 + 9 - 6)^4 & &:= (-9 + 6 - 8 + 8 + 9 - 010 + 4 + 07)^{13} \\
 &:= (-9 - 5 + 565 + 06 + 6 - 4 - 9 + 6)^4 & &:= (96 - 88 + 9 + 01 - 04 - 07)^{13} \\
 &:= (9 + 5 + 5 + 6 + 506 + 6 + 4 + 9 + 6)^4 & &:= (-9 - 68 - 8 + 90 - 1 - 04 + 07)^{13} \\
 &:= (-95 - 5 - 6 - 5 + 0664 + 9 - 6)^4 & &:= (9 + 68 + 8 - 90 + 1 + 04 + 07)^{13} \\
 &:= (-9 + 5 - 5 + 650 - 66 - 4 - 9 - 6)^4 & &:= (9 + 6 - 88 + 90 + 1 - 04 - 07)^{13} \\
 &:= (-9 - 5 + 5 + 650 - 66 - 4 - 9 - 6)^4 & &:= (9 - 6 - 88 + 90 - 1 - 04 + 07)^{13} \\
 &:= (-9 + 5 - 5 + 650 - 6 - 64 - 9 - 6)^4 & &:= (-9 + 6 + 88 - 90 + 1 + 04 + 07)^{13} \\
 &:= (-9 - 5 + 5 + 650 - 6 - 64 - 9 - 6)^4 & &:= (-96 + 8 - 8 + 90 + 10 - 4 + 07)^{13} \\
 &:= (9 + 5 + 5 - 6 + 506 - 6 + 49 - 6)^4 & &:= (-96 - 8 + 8 + 90 + 10 - 4 + 07)^{13} \\
 &:= (9 - 5 - 5 - 6 - 5 + 0664 - 96)^4 & &:= (96 + 8 - 8 - 90 - 10 + 4 + 07)^{13}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 &:= (96 - 8 + 8 - 90 - 10 + 4 + 07)^{13} \\
 &:= (9 - 68 + 8 + 90 + 1 - 040 + 7)^{13} \\
 &:= (-9 + 68 - 8 - 90 - 1 + 040 + 7)^{13} \\
 &:= (-9 - 6 + 88 - 9 - 010 - 40 - 7)^{13} \\
 &:= (9 - 68 + 89 + 010 - 40 + 7)^{13} \\
 &:= (-9 + 68 - 89 - 010 + 40 + 7)^{13} \\
 \mathbf{96947540496} &:= (9 + 6 - 9 + 4 + 7 + 540 + 4 - 9 + 6)^4 \\
 &:= (-9 + 6 + 9 + 4 + 7 + 540 + 4 - 9 + 6)^4 \\
 &:= (-9 + 6 - 9 + 4 + 7 + 540 + 4 + 9 + 6)^4 \\
 &:= (9 + 69 + 475 + 4 + 04 - 9 + 6)^4 \\
 &:= (-9 + 69 + 475 + 4 + 04 + 9 + 6)^4 \\
 &:= (-9 + 69 + 4 + 7 - 5 - 4 + 0496)^4 \\
 &:= (-9 + 69 - 4 + 7 - 5 + 4 + 0496)^4 \\
 &:= (9 + 6 + 9 + 475 + 40 + 4 + 9 + 6)^4 \\
 &:= (9 + 6 + 9 + 475 + 4 + 049 + 6)^4 \\
 &:= (9 + 6 + 9 + 47 - 5 - 4 + 0496)^4 \\
 &:= (9 + 6 - 9 + 47 + 5 + 4 + 0496)^4 \\
 &:= (-9 + 6 + 9 + 47 + 5 + 4 + 0496)^4 \\
 &:= (9 + 6 + 9 - 4 + 7 - 5 + 40 + 496)^4 \\
 &:= (9 + 6 - 9 + 4 + 7 + 5 + 40 + 496)^4 \\
 &:= (-9 + 6 + 9 + 4 + 7 + 5 + 40 + 496)^4 \\
 &:= (969 - 4 + 7 + 5 - 404 - 9 - 6)^4 \\
 &:= (96 + 9 + 47 + 5 + 404 - 9 + 6)^4 \\
 &:= (96 - 9 + 47 + 5 + 404 + 9 + 6)^4 \\
 &:= (96 + 9 + 4 + 7 - 54 + 0496)^4 \\
 &:= (9 + 69 + 4 + 75 + 404 - 9 + 6)^4 \\
 &:= (-9 + 69 + 4 + 75 + 404 + 9 + 6)^4 \\
 &:= (-9 + 69 - 4 + 7 - 5 + 404 + 96)^4 \\
 &:= (9 + 6 + 94 + 7 - 54 + 0496)^4 \\
 &:= (-9 + 6 - 9 + 475 + 40 + 49 + 6)^4 \\
 &:= (9 + 6 - 9 + 47 + 5 + 404 + 96)^4 \\
 &:= (-9 + 6 + 9 + 47 + 5 + 404 + 96)^4 \\
 &:= (-9 + 694 - 75 + 40 + 4 - 96)^4 \\
 &:= (-9 + 69 + 47 - 5 - 40 + 496)^4 \\
 &:= (9 - 6 + 94 - 75 + 40 + 496)^4 \\
 &:= (96 + 947 - 540 + 49 + 6)^4 \\
 \mathbf{97018944875} &:= (97 - 01 + 8 + 9 + 4487 - 5)^3 \\
 \mathbf{97145684173} &:= (9 + 71 + 4568 - 41 - 7 - 3)^3
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 &:= (-9 + 7 - 1 + 4568 - 41 + 73)^3 \\
 \mathbf{97272533799} &:= (9 - 727 - 2 + 5337 - 9 - 9)^3 \\
 &:= (-9 - 727 - 2 + 5337 + 9 - 9)^3 \\
 &:= (-9 - 727 - 2 + 5337 - 9 + 9)^3 \\
 \mathbf{97463015208} &:= (-9 - 7 + 4630 - 1 - 5 + 2 - 08)^3 \\
 \mathbf{97643125441} &:= (-9 + 7 - 64 + 312544 + 1)^2 \\
 \mathbf{97644375361} &:= (9 + 7 + 6 - 4 - 4 + 3 + 7 + 536 - 1)^4 \\
 &:= (9 + 7 - 6 + 4 + 4 - 3 + 7 + 536 + 1)^4 \\
 &:= (-9 + 7 + 6 + 4 + 4 + 3 + 7 + 536 + 1)^4 \\
 &:= (97 + 6 + 4 + 437 + 5 + 3 + 6 + 1)^4 \\
 &:= (-9 - 7 + 644 - 3 - 7 + 5 - 3 - 61)^4 \\
 &:= (-9 - 7 + 6 + 44 - 3 - 7 + 536 - 1)^4 \\
 &:= (-9 + 7 - 6 - 4 + 43 - 7 + 536 - 1)^4 \\
 &:= (-9 - 7 - 6 - 4 + 43 + 7 + 536 - 1)^4 \\
 &:= (-9 - 7 + 6 - 4 + 43 - 7 + 536 + 1)^4 \\
 &:= (97 - 6 + 443 - 7 - 5 + 36 + 1)^4 \\
 &:= (-9 + 76 + 443 + 7 + 5 + 36 + 1)^4 \\
 &:= (-9 + 76 - 4 + 437 - 5 + 3 + 61)^4 \\
 &:= (-9 + 76 - 4 - 4 - 37 + 536 + 1)^4 \\
 &:= (-9 + 7 + 644 - 37 - 53 + 6 + 1)^4 \\
 &:= (-9 - 7 + 644 - 37 + 5 - 36 - 1)^4 \\
 &:= (-9 + 7 + 64 + 437 + 53 + 6 + 1)^4 \\
 &:= (9 + 7 + 64 + 437 + 5 + 36 + 1)^4 \\
 &:= (-9 + 7 + 6 + 443 + 75 + 36 + 1)^4 \\
 &:= (-9 + 7 + 6 + 4 + 437 + 53 + 61)^4 \\
 &:= (976 - 44 - 375 - 3 + 6 - 1)^4 \\
 &:= (-97 + 644 - 3 + 7 - 53 + 61)^4 \\
 &:= (97 + 6 + 44 + 375 + 36 + 1)^4 \\
 &:= (97 + 6 - 44 - 37 + 536 + 1)^4 \\
 &:= (9 + 7 + 64 + 43 + 75 + 361)^4 \\
 \mathbf{97653745125} &:= (97 + 6 + 5 - 3 - 7 + 4512 - 5)^3 \\
 &:= (97 + 6 - 5 - 3 - 7 + 4512 + 5)^3 \\
 \mathbf{97663125121} &:= (-9 + 7 + 6 - 6 + 312512 + 1)^2 \\
 &:= (-9 + 7 - 6 + 6 + 312512 + 1)^2 \\
 \mathbf{97844723712} &:= (-97 - 8 - 4 + 4723 - 7 - 1 + 2)^3 \\
 &:= (9 + 78 + 4472 + 37 + 12)^3 \\
 \mathbf{97908438529} &:= (97 + 90 + 8 + 4385 + 29)^3 \\
 &:= (9 - 8265 + 321729)^2
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\mathbf{98344960000} := (-9 + 8 - 34 + 4 - 9 + 600 + 00)^4$$

$$:= (98 - 34 + 496 + 0000)^4$$

$$\mathbf{98465804768} := (98 + 46 + 5 + 8 - 04 + 7 + 6 - 8)^5$$

$$:= (98 + 46 - 5 + 8 + 04 - 7 + 6 + 8)^5$$

$$:= (98 + 46 + 5 - 8 - 04 + 7 + 6 + 8)^5$$

$$:= (98 + 4 + 65 + 8 + 04 - 7 - 6 - 8)^5$$

$$:= (98 - 4 + 65 + 8 - 04 - 7 - 6 + 8)^5$$

$$:= (98 + 4 + 65 - 8 + 04 - 7 - 6 + 8)^5$$

$$:= (98 + 4 + 6 - 5 + 80 - 4 - 7 - 6 - 8)^5$$

$$:= (98 - 4 + 6 - 5 + 80 + 4 - 7 - 6 - 8)^5$$

$$:= (98 + 4 - 6 - 5 + 80 - 4 - 7 + 6 - 8)^5$$

$$:= (98 - 4 - 6 - 5 + 80 + 4 - 7 + 6 - 8)^5$$

$$:= (98 - 4 + 6 + 5 + 8 + 047 + 6 - 8)^5$$

$$:= (98 + 4 - 6 + 5 + 8 + 047 - 6 + 8)^5$$

$$:= (98 - 4 + 6 + 5 - 8 + 047 + 6 + 8)^5$$

$$:= (98 - 4 - 6 + 5 + 8 - 04 - 7 + 68)^5$$

$$:= (98 + 4 - 6 + 5 - 8 + 04 - 7 + 68)^5$$

$$:= (98 - 4 + 6 - 5 - 8 - 04 + 7 + 68)^5$$

$$:= (9 + 84 + 6 + 58 - 04 + 7 + 6 - 8)^5$$

$$:= (9 + 84 - 6 + 58 + 04 + 7 - 6 + 8)^5$$

$$:= (-9 + 84 + 6 + 5 + 8 - 04 + 76 - 8)^5$$

$$:= (9 + 84 + 6 - 5 - 8 + 04 + 76 - 8)^5$$

$$:= (-9 + 84 + 6 + 5 - 8 - 04 + 76 + 8)^5$$

$$:= (9 + 8 + 4 + 65 + 8 - 04 + 76 - 8)^5$$

$$:= (9 + 8 - 4 + 65 + 8 + 04 + 76 - 8)^5$$

$$:= (9 + 8 + 4 + 65 - 8 - 04 + 76 + 8)^5$$

$$:= (9 - 8 + 4 + 65 + 8 - 04 + 76 + 8)^5$$

$$:= (9 + 8 - 4 + 65 - 8 + 04 + 76 + 8)^5$$

$$:= (9 - 8 - 4 + 65 + 8 + 04 + 76 + 8)^5$$

$$:= (9 + 8 - 4 + 6 - 5 + 80 - 4 + 76 - 8)^5$$

$$:= (-9 + 8 + 4 + 6 + 5 + 80 - 4 + 76 - 8)^5$$

$$:= (9 - 8 + 4 + 6 - 5 + 80 + 4 + 76 - 8)^5$$

$$:= (-9 + 8 - 4 + 6 + 5 + 80 + 4 + 76 - 8)^5$$

$$:= (9 - 8 - 4 + 6 - 5 + 80 - 4 + 76 + 8)^5$$

$$:= (-9 - 8 + 4 + 6 + 5 + 80 - 4 + 76 + 8)^5$$

$$:= (-9 - 8 + 46 + 58 - 04 + 7 + 68)^5$$

$$:= (-9 - 8 - 4 + 6 + 58 + 047 + 68)^5$$

$$:= (984 - 6 + 5 - 804 - 7 - 6 - 8)^5$$

$$:= (98 + 46 - 58 + 04 + 76 - 8)^5$$

$$:= (98 + 46 - 5 + 80 - 47 - 6 - 8)^5$$

$$:= (98 + 46 + 5 + 80 + 4 - 7 - 68)^5$$

$$:= (98 - 4 - 65 + 80 + 47 - 6 + 8)^5$$

$$:= (98 + 4 + 65 - 80 - 4 + 7 + 68)^5$$

$$:= (98 - 4 + 65 - 80 + 4 + 7 + 68)^5$$

$$:= (9 + 84 + 65 + 80 + 4 - 76 - 8)^5$$

$$:= (9 + 84 + 65 - 80 - 4 + 76 + 8)^5$$

$$:= (9 - 84 + 65 + 80 + 4 + 76 + 8)^5$$

$$:= (98 - 46 + 5 + 80 - 47 + 68)^5$$

$$:= (-98 - 4 + 65 + 80 + 47 + 68)^5$$

$$:= (9 + 846 - 5 + 80 - 4 - 768)^5$$

$$:= (-9 + 846 + 5 + 80 + 4 - 768)^5$$

$$:= (-984 + 658 + 0476 + 8)^5$$

$$\mathbf{98547108659} := (-98 + 5 + 4710 - 8 + 6 - 5 + 9)^3$$

$$:= (-98 - 5 + 4710 - 8 + 6 + 5 + 9)^3$$

$$\mathbf{98867482624} := (-9 + 88 + 6 - 7 - 4 + 8 - 2 - 6 - 2 - 4)^6$$

$$:= (-9 + 88 - 6 - 7 + 4 + 8 + 2 - 6 - 2 - 4)^6$$

$$:= (-9 + 88 - 6 - 7 - 4 + 8 - 2 + 6 - 2 - 4)^6$$

$$:= (-9 + 88 + 6 - 7 - 4 - 8 + 2 + 6 - 2 - 4)^6$$

$$:= (-9 + 88 - 6 - 7 + 4 + 8 - 2 - 6 + 2 - 4)^6$$

$$:= (-9 + 88 + 6 - 7 + 4 - 8 + 2 - 6 + 2 - 4)^6$$

$$:= (-9 + 88 + 6 - 7 - 4 - 8 - 2 + 6 + 2 - 4)^6$$

$$:= (-9 + 88 - 6 - 7 + 4 - 8 + 2 + 6 + 2 - 4)^6$$

$$:= (-9 + 88 + 6 - 7 + 4 - 8 - 2 - 6 - 2 + 4)^6$$

$$:= (-9 + 88 - 6 - 7 - 4 + 8 + 2 - 6 - 2 + 4)^6$$

$$:= (-9 + 88 - 6 - 7 + 4 - 8 - 2 + 6 - 2 + 4)^6$$

$$:= (-9 + 88 - 6 - 7 - 4 + 8 - 2 - 6 + 2 + 4)^6$$

$$:= (-9 + 88 + 6 - 7 - 4 - 8 + 2 - 6 + 2 + 4)^6$$

$$:= (-9 + 88 - 6 - 7 - 4 - 8 + 2 + 6 + 2 + 4)^6$$

$$:= (9 - 8 + 86 + 7 - 4 - 8 - 2 - 6 - 2 - 4)^6$$

$$:= (-9 + 8 + 86 - 7 - 4 + 8 - 2 - 6 - 2 - 4)^6$$

$$:= (-9 + 8 + 86 - 7 - 4 - 8 + 2 + 6 - 2 - 4)^6$$

$$:= (-9 - 8 + 86 - 7 - 4 + 8 + 2 + 6 - 2 - 4)^6$$

$$:= (-9 - 8 + 86 - 7 + 4 + 8 + 2 - 6 + 2 - 4)^6$$

$$:= (-9 + 8 + 86 - 7 - 4 - 8 - 2 + 6 + 2 - 4)^6$$

$$\begin{aligned} &:= (-9-8+86-7-4+8-2+6+2-4)^6 & &:= (9-8+8-6+7+48-2+6+2+4)^6 \\ &:= (-9+8+86-7+4-8-2-6-2+4)^6 & &:= (-9+8+8+6-7+48+2+6+2+4)^6 \\ &:= (-9-8+86-7+4+8-2-6-2+4)^6 & &:= (9-8-8+6+7+48+2+6+2+4)^6 \\ &:= (-9-8+86-7+4-8+2+6-2+4)^6 & &:= (-9+8+8-6-7+4+82-6-2-4)^6 \\ &:= (-9+8+86-7-4-8+2-6+2+4)^6 & &:= (9-8-8-6+7+4+82-6-2-4)^6 \\ &:= (-9-8+86-7-4+8+2-6+2+4)^6 & &:= (-9+8-8+6-7-4+82+6-2-4)^6 \\ &:= (-9-8+86-7+4-8-2+6+2+4)^6 & &:= (-9-8+8+6-7-4+82+6-2-4)^6 \\ &:= (-9+8+8+67-4+8+2-6-2-4)^6 & &:= (-9+8-8+6-7+4+82-6+2-4)^6 \\ &:= (-9+8+8+67+4-8-2+6-2-4)^6 & &:= (-9-8+8+6-7+4+82-6+2-4)^6 \\ &:= (-9+8-8+67+4+8-2+6-2-4)^6 & &:= (-9+8-8-6-7+4+82+6+2-4)^6 \\ &:= (-9-8+8+67+4+8-2+6-2-4)^6 & &:= (-9-8+8-6-7+4+82+6+2-4)^6 \\ &:= (-9+8+8+67-4+8-2-6+2-4)^6 & &:= (-9+8+8-6-7-4+82-6-2+4)^6 \\ &:= (-9+8+8+67-4-8+2+6+2-4)^6 & &:= (9-8-8-6+7-4+82-6-2+4)^6 \\ &:= (-9+8-8+67-4+8+2+6+2-4)^6 & &:= (-9-8-8+6-7+4+82+6-2+4)^6 \\ &:= (-9-8+8+67-4+8+2+6+2-4)^6 & &:= (-9+8-8+6-7-4+82-6+2+4)^6 \\ &:= (-9+8+8+67+4-8+2-6-2+4)^6 & &:= (-9-8+8+6-7-4+82-6+2+4)^6 \\ &:= (-9+8-8+67+4+8+2-6-2+4)^6 & &:= (-9+8-8-6-7-4+82+6+2+4)^6 \\ &:= (-9-8+8+67+4+8+2-6-2+4)^6 & &:= (-9-8+8-6-7-4+82+6+2+4)^6 \\ &:= (-9+8+8+67-4-8-2+6-2+4)^6 & &:= (9+8+8+6-7+4+8+26+2+4)^6 \\ &:= (-9+8-8+67-4+8-2+6-2+4)^6 & &:= (9+8+8+6-7-4-8-2+62-4)^6 \\ &:= (-9-8+8+67-4+8-2+6-2+4)^6 & &:= (9+8-8+6-7-4+8-2+62-4)^6 \\ &:= (-9+8+8+67+4-8-2-6+2+4)^6 & &:= (9-8+8+6-7-4+8-2+62-4)^6 \\ &:= (-9+8-8+67+4+8-2-6+2+4)^6 & &:= (-9+8+8-6+7-4+8-2+62-4)^6 \\ &:= (-9-8+8+67+4+8-2-6+2+4)^6 & &:= (-9+8+8+6+7-4-8+2+62-4)^6 \\ &:= (-9+8-8+67+4-8+2+6+2+4)^6 & &:= (9+8+8-6-7+4-8+2+62-4)^6 \\ &:= (-9-8+8+67+4-8+2+6+2+4)^6 & &:= (-9+8-8+6+7-4+8+2+62-4)^6 \\ &:= (-9-8-8+67+4+8+2+6+2+4)^6 & &:= (-9-8+8+6+7-4+8+2+62-4)^6 \\ &:= (9+8-8+6+7+48-2+6-2-4)^6 & &:= (9+8-8-6-7+4+8+2+62-4)^6 \\ &:= (9-8+8+6+7+48-2+6-2-4)^6 & &:= (9-8+8-6-7+4+8+2+62-4)^6 \\ &:= (9+8+8-6+7+48+2-6+2-4)^6 & &:= (9+8-8+6-7+4-8-2+62+4)^6 \\ &:= (9+8+8-6+7+48-2-6-2+4)^6 & &:= (9-8+8+6-7+4-8-2+62+4)^6 \\ &:= (9+8-8+6+7+48+2-6-2+4)^6 & &:= (-9+8+8-6+7+4-8-2+62+4)^6 \\ &:= (9-8+8+6+7+48+2-6-2+4)^6 & &:= (9-8-8+6-7+4+8-2+62+4)^6 \\ &:= (9+8-8-6+7+48+2+6-2+4)^6 & &:= (-9+8-8-6+7+4+8-2+62+4)^6 \\ &:= (9-8+8-6+7+48+2+6-2+4)^6 & &:= (-9-8+8-6+7+4+8-2+62+4)^6 \\ &:= (9+8-8+6+7+48-2-6+2+4)^6 & &:= (9+8+8-6-7-4-8+2+62+4)^6 \\ &:= (9-8+8+6+7+48-2-6+2+4)^6 & &:= (-9+8-8+6+7+4-8+2+62+4)^6 \\ &:= (9+8-8-6+7+48-2+6+2+4)^6 & &:= (-9-8+8+6+7+4-8+2+62+4)^6 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} &:= (9+8-8-6-7-4+8+2+62+4)^6 & &:= (9-8+8+67+4+8-26+2+4)^6 \\ &:= (9-8+8-6-7-4+8+2+62+4)^6 & &:= (9+8+8+67-4+8+2-6-24)^6 \\ &:= (-9-8-8+6+7+4+8+2+62+4)^6 & &:= (9+8+8+67+4-8-2+6-24)^6 \\ &:= (9+8+8+6-7+4+8+2+6+24)^6 & &:= (9+8-8+67+4+8-2+6-24)^6 \\ &:= (9+88+6+7-48+2+6+2-4)^6 & &:= (9-8+8+67+4+8-2+6-24)^6 \\ &:= (9+88+6+7-48-2+6-2+4)^6 & &:= (9-8-8+67-4-8+2-6+24)^6 \\ &:= (9+88+6-7-4+8-26-2-4)^6 & &:= (9+8-8-6-7+48+26+2-4)^6 \\ &:= (-9+88+6+7-4+8-26+2-4)^6 & &:= (9-8+8-6-7+48+26+2-4)^6 \\ &:= (9+88-6-7+4+8-26+2-4)^6 & &:= (9-8-8+6-7+48+26-2+4)^6 \\ &:= (9+88+6-7+4-8-26-2+4)^6 & &:= (-9+8-8-6+7+48+26-2+4)^6 \\ &:= (-9+88-6+7+4+8-26-2+4)^6 & &:= (-9-8+8-6+7+48+26-2+4)^6 \\ &:= (-9+88+6+7+4-8-26+2+4)^6 & &:= (-9-8-8+6+7+48+26+2+4)^6 \\ &:= (9+88-6-7-4+8-26+2+4)^6 & &:= (-9+8-8+6+7+48-2-6+24)^6 \\ &:= (9+88+6-7-4+8-2-6-24)^6 & &:= (-9-8+8+6+7+48-2-6+24)^6 \\ &:= (-9+88+6+7-4+8+2-6-24)^6 & &:= (9-8-8+6-7+48-2+6+24)^6 \\ &:= (9+88-6-7+4+8+2-6-24)^6 & &:= (-9+8-8-6+7+48-2+6+24)^6 \\ &:= (-9+88+6+7+4-8-2+6-24)^6 & &:= (-9-8+8-6+7+48-2+6+24)^6 \\ &:= (9+88-6-7-4+8-2+6-24)^6 & &:= (-9-8-8+6+7+48+2+6+24)^6 \\ &:= (9+88+6-7-4-8+2+6-24)^6 & &:= (-9+8+8+6+7-4+82-6-24)^6 \\ &:= (-9+88-6+7-4+8+2+6-24)^6 & &:= (9+8+8-6-7+4+82-6-24)^6 \\ &:= (9+8+86+7-48+2+6+2-4)^6 & &:= (9+8-8+6-7-4+82+6-24)^6 \\ &:= (9+8+86+7-48-2+6-2+4)^6 & &:= (9-8+8+6-7-4+82+6-24)^6 \\ &:= (9+8+86-7-4+8-26-2-4)^6 & &:= (-9+8+8-6+7-4+82+6-24)^6 \\ &:= (-9+8+86+7-4+8-26+2-4)^6 & &:= (9+8-8+6+7+4-8+26+24)^6 \\ &:= (9+8+86-7+4-8-26-2+4)^6 & &:= (9-8+8+6+7+4-8+26+24)^6 \\ &:= (9-8+86-7+4+8-26-2+4)^6 & &:= (-9+8+8+6-7+4+8+26+24)^6 \\ &:= (-9+8+86+7+4-8-26+2+4)^6 & &:= (9-8-8+6+7+4+8+26+24)^6 \\ &:= (-9-8+86+7+4+8-26+2+4)^6 & &:= (98-86+74-8+2-6-2-4)^6 \\ &:= (9+8+86-7-4+8-2-6-24)^6 & &:= (-98+86+74+8-2+6-2-4)^6 \\ &:= (-9+8+86+7-4+8+2-6-24)^6 & &:= (98-86+74-8-2-6+2-4)^6 \\ &:= (-9+8+86+7+4-8-2+6-24)^6 & &:= (-98+86+74+8+2-6-2+4)^6 \\ &:= (-9-8+86+7+4+8-2+6-24)^6 & &:= (-98+86+74+8-2-6+2+4)^6 \\ &:= (9+8+86-7-4-8+2+6-24)^6 & &:= (-98+86+74-8+2+6+2+4)^6 \\ &:= (9-8+86-7-4+8+2+6-24)^6 & &:= (98-8-6+74-82-6+2-4)^6 \\ &:= (9-8-8+67-4-8+26-2-4)^6 & &:= (-98+8+6+74+82-6-2+4)^6 \\ &:= (9+8+8+67-4+8-26+2-4)^6 & &:= (-98+8-6+74+82+6-2+4)^6 \\ &:= (9+8+8+67+4-8-26+2+4)^6 & &:= (-98-8+6+74+82+6+2+4)^6 \\ &:= (9+8-8+67+4+8-26+2+4)^6 & &:= (9+88-67+48+2-6-2-4)^6 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 &:= (9 + 88 - 67 + 48 - 2 - 6 + 2 - 4)^6 & &:= (-9 - 8 + 8 - 67 - 4 + 82 + 62 + 4)^6 \\
 &:= (-9 + 88 + 67 + 4 - 82 + 6 - 2 - 4)^6 & &:= (-9 + 8 + 8 + 67 + 4 - 8 - 26 + 24)^6 \\
 &:= (-9 + 88 + 67 - 4 - 82 + 6 - 2 + 4)^6 & &:= (-9 + 8 - 8 + 67 + 4 + 8 - 26 + 24)^6 \\
 &:= (-9 + 88 + 67 + 4 - 82 - 6 + 2 + 4)^6 & &:= (-9 - 8 + 8 + 67 + 4 + 8 - 26 + 24)^6 \\
 &:= (-9 - 88 + 67 + 4 + 82 + 6 + 2 + 4)^6 & &:= (9 + 8 - 8 + 6 + 7 + 48 - 26 + 24)^6 \\
 &:= (-9 + 88 - 67 + 4 - 8 + 2 + 62 - 4)^6 & &:= (9 - 8 + 8 + 6 + 7 + 48 - 26 + 24)^6 \\
 &:= (-9 + 88 - 67 - 4 - 8 + 2 + 62 + 4)^6 & &:= (98 + 8 - 6 - 74 - 8 + 26 + 24)^6 \\
 &:= (9 - 88 + 67 + 4 + 8 + 2 + 62 + 4)^6 & &:= (98 - 8 - 6 - 74 + 8 + 26 + 24)^6 \\
 &:= (9 + 88 + 6 - 7 - 48 + 26 - 2 - 4)^6 & &:= (9 + 886 - 7 + 4 - 826 - 2 + 4)^6 \\
 &:= (-9 + 88 + 6 + 7 - 48 + 26 + 2 - 4)^6 & &:= (-9 + 886 + 7 + 4 - 826 + 2 + 4)^6 \\
 &:= (9 + 88 - 6 - 7 - 48 + 26 + 2 + 4)^6 & &:= (9 - 88 + 67 + 48 + 26 + 2 + 4)^6 \\
 &:= (9 + 88 - 6 - 7 + 48 + 2 - 62 - 4)^6 & &:= (9 - 88 + 67 + 48 + 2 + 6 + 24)^6 \\
 &:= (-9 + 88 - 6 + 7 + 48 - 2 - 62 + 4)^6 & &:= (-9 + 88 - 67 + 4 + 82 - 6 - 24)^6 \\
 &:= (9 + 88 + 6 - 7 - 48 + 2 - 6 + 24)^6 & &:= (9 + 88 + 67 + 4 - 82 + 6 - 24)^6 \\
 &:= (9 + 88 - 6 - 7 - 48 + 2 + 6 + 24)^6 & &:= (9 + 88 - 67 - 4 - 8 + 26 + 24)^6 \\
 &:= (9 + 88 + 6 - 7 - 4 - 82 + 62 - 4)^6 & &:= (-9 + 88 - 6 - 7 - 48 + 26 + 24)^6 \\
 &:= (-9 + 88 - 6 + 7 + 4 - 82 + 62 + 4)^6 & &:= (9 + 8 + 867 + 4 - 826 + 2 + 4)^6 \\
 &:= (-9 - 88 + 6 + 7 + 4 + 82 + 62 + 4)^6 & &:= (98 + 86 - 74 + 8 - 26 - 24)^6 \\
 &:= (-9 + 88 + 6 - 7 - 4 - 8 + 26 - 24)^6 & &:= (-98 + 86 + 74 + 8 - 26 + 24)^6 \\
 &:= (-9 + 88 - 6 - 7 - 4 + 8 - 26 + 24)^6 & &:= (-98 + 8 - 674 + 826 + 2 + 4)^6 \\
 &:= (9 + 8 + 86 - 7 - 48 + 26 - 2 - 4)^6 & &:= (-9 - 88 + 67 + 48 + 26 + 24)^6 \\
 &:= (-9 + 8 + 86 + 7 - 48 + 26 + 2 - 4)^6 & &:= (-9 + 8 + 867 + 4 - 826 + 24)^6 \\
 &:= (9 - 8 + 86 - 7 + 48 - 2 - 62 + 4)^6 & &:= (9 - 8 - 8 - 67 - 482 + 624)^6 \\
 &:= (-9 - 8 + 86 + 7 + 48 + 2 - 62 + 4)^6 & & \mathbf{99381523968} := (9938 + 1 - 5239 - 68)^3 \\
 &:= (9 + 8 + 86 - 7 - 48 + 2 - 6 + 24)^6 & & \mathbf{99445904137} := (-9 + 94 + 4590 - 4 - 1 - 37)^3 \\
 &:= (9 + 8 + 86 - 7 - 4 - 82 + 62 - 4)^6 & & \mathbf{99574747875} := (-9 - 9 + 5 - 7 + 4747 - 87 - 5)^3 \\
 &:= (9 + 8 - 86 - 7 + 4 + 82 + 62 - 4)^6 & & \quad \quad \quad := (-9 - 9 - 5 - 7 + 4747 - 87 + 5)^3 \\
 &:= (9 - 8 + 86 - 7 + 4 - 82 + 62 + 4)^6 & & \mathbf{99747325584} := (-9 - 9747 + 325584)^2 \\
 &:= (9 + 8 - 86 - 7 - 4 + 82 + 62 + 4)^6 & & \mathbf{99757432336} := (9 - 9 - 7 + 574 + 3 - 2 + 3 - 3 - 6)^4 \\
 &:= (-9 + 8 + 86 - 7 - 4 - 8 + 26 - 24)^6 & & \quad \quad \quad := (-9 + 9 - 7 + 574 + 3 - 2 + 3 - 3 - 6)^4 \\
 &:= (-9 - 8 + 86 - 7 - 4 + 8 + 26 - 24)^6 & & \quad \quad \quad := (-9 - 9 + 7 + 574 + 3 + 2 + 3 - 3 - 6)^4 \\
 &:= (9 + 8 + 8 + 67 - 48 + 26 + 2 - 4)^6 & & \quad \quad \quad := (9 - 9 - 7 + 574 + 3 - 2 - 3 + 3 - 6)^4 \\
 &:= (9 - 8 - 8 + 67 - 48 - 2 + 62 - 4)^6 & & \quad \quad \quad := (-9 + 9 - 7 + 574 + 3 - 2 - 3 + 3 - 6)^4 \\
 &:= (9 + 8 - 8 + 67 + 48 + 2 - 62 + 4)^6 & & \quad \quad \quad := (-9 - 9 + 7 + 574 + 3 + 2 - 3 + 3 - 6)^4 \\
 &:= (9 - 8 + 8 + 67 + 48 + 2 - 62 + 4)^6 & & \quad \quad \quad := (9 - 9 - 7 + 574 - 3 - 2 + 3 + 3 - 6)^4 \\
 &:= (-9 + 8 - 8 - 67 + 4 + 82 + 62 - 4)^6 & & \quad \quad \quad := (-9 + 9 - 7 + 574 - 3 - 2 + 3 + 3 - 6)^4 \\
 &:= (-9 - 8 + 8 - 67 + 4 + 82 + 62 - 4)^6 & & \quad \quad \quad := (-9 - 9 + 7 + 574 - 3 + 2 + 3 + 3 - 6)^4 \\
 &:= (-9 + 8 - 8 - 67 - 4 + 82 + 62 + 4)^6 & & \quad \quad \quad := (9 - 9 - 7 + 574 - 3 - 2 - 3 - 3 + 6)^4
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} & := (-9 + 9 - 7 + 574 - 3 - 2 - 3 - 3 + 6)^4 \\ & := (-9 - 9 + 7 + 574 - 3 + 2 - 3 - 3 + 6)^4 \\ & := (-9 - 9 - 7 + 574 + 3 - 2 + 3 + 3 + 6)^4 \\ & := (99 + 7 + 5 + 7 + 432 + 3 + 3 + 6)^4 \\ & := (9 + 97 + 5 + 7 + 432 + 3 + 3 + 6)^4 \\ & := (9 + 9 - 7 + 574 + 3 - 23 + 3 - 6)^4 \\ & := (9 + 9 - 7 + 574 - 3 - 23 - 3 + 6)^4 \\ & := (9 - 9 - 7 + 574 - 32 + 33 - 6)^4 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} & := (-9 + 9 - 7 + 574 - 32 + 33 - 6)^4 \\ & := (-9 - 9 + 7 + 574 + 32 + 3 - 36)^4 \\ & := (99 + 75 + 74 + 323 - 3 - 6)^4 \\ & := (99 + 75 + 7 + 43 + 2 + 336)^4 \\ & := (99 + 7 + 57 + 432 + 3 - 36)^4 \\ & := (9 + 97 + 57 + 432 + 3 - 36)^4 \\ & := (-99 + 757 - 432 + 336)^4 \end{aligned}$$

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